

the colors of care

Design & Emotion 2014
9th international conference | Colombia

Organizers:

the Design & Emotion Society raises issues and facilitates dialogue among practitioners, researchers, and industry in order to integrate salient themes of emotional experience into the design profession.

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of care

Design & Emotion 2014
9th international conference | Colombia

October 6-10/2014. Bogota, Cali & Medellin. Colombia

International Conference on Design and Emotion (9th : 2014 : Colombia)

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Corrección de estilo
Matthew Battle, Tiziana Laudato y María del Mar Ravassa

Diseño y diagramación:
Angélica Ramos, Adriana Páramo
Taller de Medios. Facultad de Arquitectura y Diseño. Universidad de los Andes

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Design & Emotion 2014
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diseño • emoción • innovación

October 6-10/2014. Bogota, Cali & Medellin. Colombia

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Editorial

These are the proceedings of the 9th International Conference on Design & Emotion, “The Colors of Care,” October 6-10, 2014. This conference is a forum held every second year where practitioners, researchers, and industry leaders meet to exchange knowledge and insights concerning the cross-disciplinary field of design and emotion. For this edition of the conference, the programme committee tried to raise the discussion on Design, Emotion and Social Innovation, by inviting submissions that addressed complex societal problems such as education, fair trade, sanitation, pollution, women’s rights, climate change. The proceedings provide you with an overview of all presented workshops, research papers, design cases, and posters.

For its first visit to Latin America, the Design & Emotion Conference is hosted by the Design Department of the Universidad de los Andes in Bogotá, Colombia. In conjunction with Universidad de los Andes, two other Colombian design schools hosted conference workshops on October 6 and 7: Universidad Icesi in the city of Cali and EAFIT University in the city of Medellín.

The call for papers attracted 200 submissions from researchers of communities such as social sciences, humanities, engineering, computer science, HCI, psychology, health sciences, marketing and business. After a double-blind review process, in which each submission was reviewed by at least two of 104 expert reviewers from 21 countries, 56% of the submissions were accepted. These submissions were included in a rich program of oral presentations, workshops and open discussions to be held by 95 delegates from 22 countries accompanied by four leading-edge keynote speakers.

We thank the authors for choosing to disseminate their research at this conference. In addition, we would like to thank the reviewers, copyeditors, designers, and all the other people who have been instrumental in assuring the high quality of papers published in these proceedings.

We wish you an inspiring conference and hope that you will have the chance to experience your colors of care.

The Program Committee

Conference Themes

Design and Emotion has been consistently the conference's overarching theme. This time the organizing committee opens the discussion on Design, Emotion and Social Innovation.

A solution for society's complex problems such as education, fair trade, sanitation, pollution, women's rights, climate change falls beyond commercial needs or market rules. From a social innovation standpoint any solution to these problems is a matter of social impact. Design practitioners and researchers could contribute by leveraging on their naturally emphatic methods of understanding people's emotions, culture and social practices.

The conference's general theme has five sub-themes that cover a vast variety of contemporary concerns about emotion and design. The conference presents rich and original contributions aligned to the following topics:

SUB-THEME 1 Design for Social Innovation

DESCRIPTION	Aspects of innovative communities that promote not only technical or economical changes but mainly deep cultural changes and positive collective emotions
INCLUDES THESE TOPICS:	Cultural Industries Social Business Socially Responsive/Responsible Design Identity and Cultural values Social Innovation and the User Experience

SUB-THEME 2 Theoretical Issues of Design and Emotion

DESCRIPTION	Relationships between the philosophical and theoretical foundations of human emotions and design
INCLUDES THESE TOPICS:	Philosophical and Theoretical Foundations Aesthetics and Meaning of the Experience Desires, Motivations and Values Space and Time Situation and context

SUB-THEME 3 Methodological Issues of Design and Emotion

DESCRIPTION	Methods for the detection, assessment and application of human emotions
INCLUDES THESE TOPICS:	Trans-disciplinary Methodologies Co-creation and Participatory Design Open Source and Design Persuasive Design end Behavioral Change Methods for Social Innovation Corporate Identity and Branding Retail Design Service Design

SUB-THEME 4 Well-being and Sustainability

DESCRIPTION	Preservation of positive social, economic, psychological and medical states
INCLUDES THESE TOPICS:	Design & Well-Being (incl. food, healthcare & love) Sustainable Lifestyle Confidence belonging and Reassurance Well-being and the senses

SUB-THEME 5 Experience and Interaction

DESCRIPTION	Mediated and unmediated experiences between collectives of people or individuals interacting products and services
INCLUDES THESE TOPICS:	Product Service Systems Experience Design Product Perception and Sensation Human Factors & HCI

Conference Organizers

The 9th International Conference on Design & Emotion is organized by:

Universidad de los Andes

(www.uniandes.edu.co)

Since the Universidad de los Andes was founded in 1948, it has been committed to developing intellectual, technical and humanist leadership, and has played an active role in the production of thought, science, and progress in Colombia.

The University is a private non-profit institution that fosters pluralism, diversity, dialogue, debate, criticism, tolerance and respect for ideas, beliefs and values. Likewise, it promotes academic excellence and offers its students a critical, ethical and well-rounded education. The Universidad de los Andes has developed its own educational project, in order to achieve the highest standards in its disciplines and to contribute to the cultural and economic development of the country. In order to do this, the University provides an interdisciplinary environment with the flexibility required for the articulation of arts, sciences, humanities and technology.

Universidad Icesi

(www.icesi.edu.co)

Icesi University was founded in 1979 and is presently recognized as one of Colombia's most important universities. It strives incessantly for: high quality education, a culture of continuous research and student motivation in favor of good work ethics and entrepreneurship. Icesi University consists of five schools offering eleven master programs, nine medical-surgical specialties and nineteen undergraduate programs, including Industrial Design and Interactive Media Design.

Its campus, with an area of 124,701 m², is located in Cali, Colombia, and it supports a current enrollment of 5,630 students: 4,763 in undergraduate programs and 900 in graduate programs. 184 full time professors and 390 associate professors constitute our body of teaching staff. Of the full time professors, 63% hold a title of PhD, and the others are currently doctoral candidates.

Universidad EAFIT

(www.eafit.edu.co)

EAFIT is a university with a 52-year history that is constantly growing, transcending regional and national boundaries and connecting with the world. Today EAFIT is a place where quality, pertinence and values are encapsulated in our institutional mission to form better women and men who contribute to the country's social, economic and scientific progress. As a guarantee of that excellence, those who have entrusted their academic and personal development to EAFIT can take comfort in the high-quality Institutional Accreditation the university has received from the National Education Ministry, valid until 2018. The five schools offer three doctorates, 21 master's degree programs, 64 graduate certificate programs and 20 undergraduate degree programs.

All of this occurs on a campus that some time ago was transformed into a University-Park, a place for students to spend and share time with their peers in an environment abundant in native flora and fauna. The campus supports a current enrollment of 9,153 students in undergraduate programs and 2,871 in graduate programs. 103 full time professors and 59 associate professors constitute our body of teaching staff. 73% of them hold a PhD.

International Design & Emotion Society

(www.designandemotion.org)

The Design & Emotion Society raises issues and facilitates dialogue among practitioners, researchers, and industry in order to integrate salient themes of emotional experience into the design profession.

The Design & Emotion Society was established in 1999 as an international network of researchers, designers, and companies sharing an interest in experience-driven design. The network is used to exchange insights, research, tools, and methods that support the involvement of emotional experience in product design. The daily board is based in the Netherlands. Although the initiative originated from the discipline of product design and design research, through the years practitioners from other design disciplines such as interaction design and branding design have contributed to and benefited from the network and its activities.

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Keynote speakers

RODOLFO LLINÁS *Professor of Neuroscience and Chairman of the Department of Physiology*

Rodolfo Llinás is the Thomas and Suzanne Murphy Professor of Neuroscience and Chairman of the Department of Physiology and Neuroscience at the NYU School of Medicine. Llinás has written ten books and has published numerous papers in medicine and science.

He has also chaired the NASA/NeuroLab Science Working Group and has been recognized with honorary doctorates as well as numerous prizes and commendations.

CYNTHIA E. SMITH *Industrial Designer*

Cynthia E. Smith serves as Cooper-Hewitt, National Design Museum's Curator of Socially Responsible Design, in New York. Trained as an industrial designer, for over a decade she led multi-disciplinary design and planning projects for cultural institutions, and after earning a graduate degree at Harvard University's Kennedy School of Government joined Cooper-Hewitt, where she integrates her work experience with her advocacy on human rights and social justice issues.

She co-authored *The Politics of Genocide: U.S. Rhetoric vs. Inaction in Darfur* for the Kennedy School Review; co-organized the Social Impact Design Summit, white paper and public forum; curates the *Design with the Other 90%* exhibition series and co-curated the 2010 Design Triennial: *Why Design Now?* Named a "20/20 New Pioneer" by *Icon* design magazine, she is one of *Metropolis* magazine's "next generation of curators"; she has served on numerous international design juries and lectured widely on socially responsible design.

ALBERTO MANTILLA *Industrial Designer*

Was born in Bogota, Colombia and graduated with a BA in Industrial Design from Javeriana University in 1983. Alberto worked for Henry Dreyfuss Associates before co-founding Curve ID with Anthony Baxter in 1994. Curve ID is a design consultancy with a wide range of well known clients including: Nike, John Deere, Pyrex and Colgate Palmolive. In 2001 he co-founded Mint Inc with Anthony Baxter and Scott Henderson.

Alberto's work has been the subject of numerous design articles including TIME magazine's "Best Designs of the Year" article in 1998 and has won many design awards including two prestigious IDEA awards, ID Magazine's "Design Distinction" award, and a Colombian Lápiz de Acero award.

JOACHIM SAUTER *Media Artist and Designer*

After graduating from the academy of fine arts in Berlin, Joachim Sauter studied at the 'German Academy for Film and Television', Berlin. Since the early 1980's, he has been working as a media artist and designer. From the beginning, Joachim Sauter has focussed on digital technologies and is experimenting how they can be used to express content, form, and narration. Fuelled by this interest, he founded ART+COM in 1988 together with other artists, designers, scientists and technologists.

Their goal was to practically research this new up-and-coming medium in the realm of art and design. Until now, he is leading this interdisciplinary group. In the course of his work he was invited to participate on many exhibitions. Since 1991 he is full professor for "New Media Art and Design" at the 'University of the Arts' Berlin and since 2001 adjunct professor at UCLA, Los Angeles.

Papers

SUB-THEME 1. Design for Social Innovation

Aspects of innovative communities that promote not only technical or economical changes but mainly deep cultural changes and positive collective emotions

Full papers

Subversive Interaction Design Digital Design and Inspiration

Foad Hamidi, Melanie Baljko

Learning Advanced Finnish: Explorations For Second Language Acquisition

Tania Rodriguez-Kaarto, Young-Ae Hahn

The Oral Patrimony of a Community in The Construction of Creative and Cultural Industries: A Strategy for Cultural Sustainability and Economic Growth

Tania Delgado

Disrupting Health And Social Care By Design

Paul A. Rodgers, Andy Tennant, Katie Dodd

Design Emotion Brand Images Enhance Social Value, Inspire Change and Intensify Social Transformation

Stephen T.F. Poon

Feeding Your Piggy Bank with Intentions: A Study on Saving Behaviour, Saving Strategies, and Happiness

Santiago De Francisco Vela, Mafalda Casais, Prof.Dr.Ir Pieter Desmet

Demand Responsive Transport as a Social Innovation. The Case of Skewiel Mobiel

H. (Rick) Schotman and G.D.S. (Geke) Ludden

In the Making: Material and Immaterial Transformations In Colombian Indigenous Communities

Emilia Atuesta Pradilla

Craft and Faith-Based Souvenirs. The Case of Two Cities in Turkey

Dilek Akbulut

Shared Value as a Contributor to Social Innovation

María De Los Ángeles González Pérez, Freddy Zapata Vanegas, Javier Francisco Silva Salazar, Santiago Restrepo Barrera

The Construction of a Collective Memory of Urban Space: Exploring the Experiences Reported by Cyclists in Recife - Brazil

William Guedes Lins Júnior, Gabriela G. Jesumary, Kátia Medeiros Araújo

From: Government, To: Citizens - Writing With Care -

Miguel Gandour, Carlos Ortiz, Diana Rocha, Cristina Mejía, Marcela Ángel

Troca.Cc: An Enabling Platform for the Development of Social Innovation in Cali, Colombia

Javier Aguirre Ramos

Short papers

Making, Emotion and the Drive to Re-Shore Uk Garment Manufacturing

Douglas Atkinson

Design cases

Simple Limb Institute. An Affordable Prosthesis for Everyone

Gerhardt Reichert, Leslie Speer

Peerby.Com. Borrow The Things You Need from the People in Your Neighborhood

Anna Noyons

Zonea/Zone1: Reflection/Resilience

David Frisco, Andrew Shea

Design of Interactions for Social Appropriation of Knowledge

José Augusto Ocampo A.

Posturaroma - The Embodiment of Safety

Marco Van Hout, Laura Mul, Loes Bogers, Shinichiro Ito

Workshops

Design for Happiness & Sustainable Societies

Carolina Escobar-Tello

Playful City Jam

Valentina Vezzani, Tang Tang, Fabrizio Pierandrei

Dibujando la pobreza, coloreamos la paz

Natalia Currea, Carolina Ávila, Mariana Amatullo, Francisco José Noguera, Ignacio Vidal

Language of Conflicts: An Introduction to Using Concern Conflicts as a Design Opportunity

Deger Ozkaramanli, Elif Özcan, Pieter Desmet

SUB-THEME 2. Theoretical Issues of Design and Emotion

Relationships between the philosophical and theoretical foundations of human emotions and design

Full papers

Timelessness In Sustainable Product Design

Alex Lobos

The Effects of Context in Product Color Testing

Bryan Howell, Estefanía Marín, Soojeong Kook

Life-Cycle Interactions for Modelling Human Emotions. A Foundation for Developing 'Design For Emotion' Support Tools

Jonathan C. Borg, Lawrence Farrugia

Emotional and Rational Aspects of the Morphogenesis of Multimedia Presentation

Anna Zyrianova

Sharing Imagination and Emotion through the Use of Lively Interactive Products

Kenny K. N. Chow, Phd

Designing for Self-Actualization in Childhood

Tatiana Mejía Piedrahita

Craftsmanship Precepts For Design Practice

Ana Luíza Cerqueira Freitas, Lucas Monteiro Rocha Faria

Pleasantness and Arousal in Twenty-Five Positive Emotions Elicited by Durable Products

Juan Carlos Ortíz Nicolás, Marco Aurisicchio, Pieter M.A. Desmet

In the Eye of the Patient Individual Differences in Emotional Reactions to Visual Design Aesthetics Of Health-Care Products

John Magnus Roos

Aesthetic Balance in Three Different Emotions

Carlos Córdoba-Cely

Short papers

Evaluating Product Perception Using Eye-Tracking and Semantic Scales: Comparing Real and Virtual Representations

Juan Carlos Rojas-López, Manuel Contero, Jaime Guixeres, Mauricio Hincapié

Design and Emotion into Collective Public Use Products?

Gabriela Zubarán Pizzato, Dr., Lia Buarque De Macedo Guimarães, Phd

Empathy Expression and Development in Industrial Design Education

Fabio Andrés Téllez

Sub-Theme 3. Methodological Issues of Design and Emotion

Methods for the detection, assessment and application of human emotions

Full papers

Appraisals to Light: A Framework to Study Emotion in Retail Spaces

Bhakti Sharma, Leandro Miletto Tonetto

Sensorial Groups as a Tool to Integrate the Emotional Dimension in Design

Deyanira Bedolla Pereda

How Deep is Deep? A Four-Layer Model of Insights into Human Needs for Design Innovation

Mieke Van Der Bijl-Brouwer, Kees Dorst

Integral Design Tutoring Model as a Knowledge Transfer Strategy for Smes in Colombia

Javier Ricardo Mejía Sarmiento, José Emilio Jiménez Ibañez, Daniela Chavarría Devia

Enhancing the Value of Social Innovation: Introducing the ‘People Value Canvas’ to Support Designers in Value Creation

Sabine E Wildevuur, Dick Van Dijk, Marise Schot

Studying Retail Design through a Cross-Cultural Perspective

Ann Petermans, Ammin Gil Huerta

Capturing Conflict Experiences. Five Methods for Identifying Intrapersonal Concern Conflicts

Deger Ozkaramanli, Elif Özcan, Pieter M. A. Desmet

Emotional Design through Measurement of Psychophysiological and Behavioral Parameters: Taking Steps Towards Neurodesign

Noé González Monestina, Daniel Puente Berdasco, María Begoña Jorda Albiñana, Teresa Magal Royo

Say, What Did You See? A Qualitative Interview Reveals How Users Interpreted Gui Icons

Martha Skogen

Experiences and Senses. An Experimental Based Methodology for the Design Optimization

Elia Gatti, Monica Bordegoni, Serena Camere

Feeler Reflection Game. A Case Study on a Design Game for Participatory Design

Eva Durall, Teemu Leinonen, Juan Fernando González

Visual Workflows for Design Project Knowledge Management

Jaime Rivera, Yassine Abouhazim, Laura Mattis, Stan Ruecker, Patricia Wang

The Future of Textiles Sourcing: Exploring the Potential for Digital Tools

Bruna Petreca, Douglas Atkinson, Nadia Bianchi-Berthouze, Dominic Furniss, Sharon Baurley

“Rhetorical Ability”: Reason, Emotion, and Character as Heuristics for the Evaluation of Efficacy in Design

G. Mauricio Mejía, Sauman Chu

Run for Your Life! Using Emotion Theory in Designing for Concrete Product Interactions

Steven F. Fokkinga, Pieter M.A. Desmet

Nonverbal Usability Tests with Emotions for the Visually Impaired

Carlos Henrique Berg, Luciane Maria Fadel, Vânia Ribas Ulbricht, Dra.

Get On Board! Educational Design for Early Childhood, Approached as Interdisciplinary Participation

Diana C. Casalins Petro, Ketty Miranda Orozco, Tatiana Miranda Orozco

Experimenting With Materials – A Source for Designers to Give Meaning to New Applications

Camilo Ayala García

Short papers

Applying Systemic Design on Human Processes. A First Approach to Sustainable Anthrop-O-Systems

Daniela Restrepo Ortiz

Appraisal Analysis to Design Process: A Case Study on Education

Jussana Ramos Dos Santos, Leandro Miletto Tonetto

Movement and Experiences in Constructed Spaces. A Description of Spatial Experiences, Based on Movement

Liselotte Vroman, Thierry Lagrange

Are You Going to Wear your Wearable for Life? Designing for Long-Term Social Health

Shin Sano, Sarah Rosenbach, Claudia Strenger

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Just a Moment, Please!. Improving the Overall User Experience, Moment by Moment

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Affective Decisions and Recommender Systems

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SUBTHEME 1 Design for Social Innovation

The social and cultural wealth that characterize the quality of life of a community lie in the community's economic and political practices, social capital, aesthetic enjoyment and cultural integration. Innovative communities promote not only technical or economical changes but mainly deep cultural changes and positive collective emotions.

Includes these topics:

- Cultural Industries and Social Business
- Socially Responsive/Responsible Design
- Identity and Cultural Values
- E-governance and Digital Citizenship
- Design Policies

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SUBVERSIVE INTERACTION DESIGN DIGITAL DESIGN AND INSPIRATION

Foad Hamidi, Melanie Baljko
GaMaY Lab, Lassonde School of Engineering
York University, Toronto, Canada
✉ fhamidi@cse.yorku.ca, mb@cse.yorku.ca

ABSTRACT

Subversion is a stance that questions, challenges, and transforms extant prevalent social dynamics, potentially mediated by interactive digital media. Here, we discuss this approach, drawing across disciplinary boundaries (Design, Human-Computer Interaction, and the Maker Movement), illustrated with three design examples. Our aim is to draw into focus the following three aspects of design: (i) looking to cultural artifacts for inspiration, (ii) fabrication approaches that emphasize repurposing and rearrangement of technologies, and (iii) critical reflection.

KEYWORDS: *Interaction Design, Value-Sensitive Design, Critical Making.*

INTRODUCTION

Löwgren & Stolterman (2004, page no.12) stated that the ‘... designer needs to be critical toward any description of the design process and to appropriate aspects of it rather than adopt it completely’. Here, we advocate the appropriation of techniques in service of subversion, drawing across the disciplinary boundaries of Design, Human-Computer Interaction, and the Maker Movement.

The term *subversion* has been used in various contexts, but here we adopt the term in a positive and constructive sense as, for example, used by Neil Postman in his book, *Teaching as Subversive Activity* (2009). Subversive activity encourages reimagining the relationship of users with technology and, in many cases, is not so much a design as a redesign method. This postmodern view values the rearrangement and redefinition of meanings within extant technologies, and so bears kinship with the Maker and Hacker subcultures that also encourage radical examination and reuse of extant designs (Levy, 2001; Anderson, 2012). The term *subversion* here is not meant in the sense that taps into the rhetoric of hegemony, but rather to align with the stance of questioning, challenging, and transforming extant prevalent social dynamics, as mediated by technology.

Historical cultural artifacts refer to entities created by individuals or groups that embody information about a culture (Murchison, 2010). Whereas many cultural artifacts are physical objects (e.g., the Tibetan prayer wheel), they can also

include cultural and artistic processes and their outcomes (e.g., practices and traditions of collaborative and performative poetry). Via an ethnographic approach, these objects *in situ* are probes for culture and community, given the Activity Theory based view of the individual as a socially situated entity who is always part of a community (Nardi, 1995). These artifacts are simply the technologies of a prior time, and have persisted and gained prevalence, due to the social or cultural values and practices that they support or otherwise mediate, whether these are seen as positive or negative — for instance, consider the artifact of the Guillotine and its role in the Reign of Terror (Hunt et al., 2010). Be this as it may, these artifacts, when examined through the lens of their contexts of use, can be sources of information that can inspire and/or animate the design of digital interactive media.

Making

The hacking subculture, as developed around the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) in the ‘50s and ‘60s, refers to a unique approach and attitude towards the design and implementation of technology, and especially computer hardware and software that emphasizes sharing, a challenge to authority, playful cleverness, and decentralization of technological resources (Levy, 2001). An important part of the hacker approach is the belief that technology should be used to improve life conditions, specifically through the democratization of access to information. An important consequence of this idea has been the development of both virtual and actual

mechanisms such as technology clubs, social networks, free tutorials, and support forums that provide practical information on how to develop and utilize technology. Thus, hacking is as much about praxis as it is about community. This emphasis on community is also present in the closely related, Maker Movement, which advocates the reuse of information and techniques, and the sharing of ideas. The term 'Maker Movement' loosely refers to the proliferation of individuals who use both novel (e.g., 3D printing) and traditional (e.g., glassblowing) manufacturing methods to subvert the mass production factory model, and engage directly with every stage of the creation of their customized small batch designs. This movement has been greatly empowered, if not made entirely possible, by a democratization of manufacturing brought about by recent technological advances. Makers encourage users to become creators themselves and question and rearrange existing designs as they see fit (Anderson, 2012). The Maker Movement has afforded prominence and accessibility to hands-on crafting and manufacturing techniques for the actualization of DIY designs. New technologies such as open-source hardware (Davidson, 2004; Igoe, 2011), and 3D printing have been instrumental to the success of making digital objects (Anderson, 2012).

Another aspect of the Maker Movement is how it draws into focus the role of those individuals engaged in creation and small-scale fabrication. Prior debate focused on the roles (in complement or in tension) between 'design' as conducted by those with different types of training: those from a Design background (e.g., receiving training from a Design school, typically but not exclusively drawing upon an Art or Architecture context) as opposed to those from a Human-Computer Interaction background (e.g., receiving training in Social Psychology, Cognitive Science, and/or Computer Science). For instance, see Don Norman's essay 'Why Design Education Must Change' (2012). For the sake of brevity, we will not address the issue here except to point out that the role of those in DIY maker spaces is increasingly recognized as one of a serious practitioner, with features of critical engagement and novel, open innovation (as opposed to merely amateur expertise) (Lindtner et al., 2014). And of course there is the flourishing brand of 'Design Thinking', as colonized in business schools. The issue of nomenclature for roles in the design process — to wit, who counts as a 'Designer' — is likely intractable and irrevocably bound up in issues of professionalization and credentialing. Regardless of label, we feel that those engaged in activities that can be broadly considered design should realize and take up the potential role as powerful social actors that can question and influence social values through their designs. We recognize, as practitioners of research-creation in an academic research lab, that there is a particular impetus to do so. The context of academic practice affords particularly unique opportunities for social activism via the process of design research-creation. Aspects of this context include a different set of process objectives and goals, resourcing via institutional support, and research agency funding (the adjudication of which is quite different from those operating in a business context), the mode of dissemination via peer-review,

and the opportunities for deployment via knowledge mobilization and technology transfer.

The Critical Stance

Over the last decade, stances that are rooted in critical theory have increasingly been applied to the design processes and outcomes in HCI. The stance advocates increasing awareness and critical reflection on the hidden assumptions, ideologies, and values underlying technology design, and might be seen as the HCI complement to Critical Design (Dunne, 1999; Raby, 2001). For instance, Löwgren and Stolterman (2004) advocated, through the *Thoughtful Interaction Design* approach, a stance that not only focuses on technology but also on the context of use, foregrounding the key observation that interaction designers are in the business of affording dynamic processes of interaction (rather than static objects). In their approach, they promote thoughtful and reflective processes that allow the designer to be responsible for the functional qualities of the design product, alongside its other qualities, such as ethical and aesthetic. Another related stance, *Reflective Design*, recognizes the importance of reflecting on the unconscious values embedded in computing and the practices it supports (Sengers, 2005). This method encourages all stakeholders, designers and users, to use reflection and participate in the critical design and use of digital artifacts. Both of these stances identify the role of the designers of digital technologies as potential shapers of social behavior through these technologies, and thus should bring social awareness to the process. To this end, designers are social and cultural activists, who, through creating designs that question authority, raise awareness and provide alternative points of view. Thus, designers should exercise reflection and ask questions examining different aspects of their design at every stage (Löwgren & Stolterman, 2004; Sengers, 2005).

The activity of critical reflection requires engaged knowledge about the users of the design and the context in which it is going to be used, which can arise from a number of sources. Certainly there is the designer's own experience. This approach is a common feature in the Maker and Hacker communities in which, oftentimes, designers are motivated to improve or replace an inadequate design arising from first-hand experience. Direct engagement of the interaction designer with their designs can reveal issues that are difficult to detect using other inquiry techniques (Johanasson & Linde, 2005). Reflection on this mode of direct engagement with interaction and design is now increasingly undertaken (Treadaway, 2007; Efimova, 2009). The widespread adoption of user-centered design (UCD) approaches reveals the utility of frequent and longitudinal occasions for user observation and engagement for, among other reasons, access to information. In our cross-cultural design work, we have also employed the approach of using Human Access Points (HAPs) (Marsden et al., 2008). A HAP, originally developed in the context of deploying ICT in developing countries, refers to a local 'guide' who is a collaborator in the development of culturally-relevant technological solutions for a specific community.

FROM RESEARCH TO PRACTICE

Synchrum

Project: How might the boundaries between the social roles of performer and audience member be blurred? How might members of an audience be afforded new opportunities to engage with each other and in a performance?

Discovery: While travelling in China and India, we became aware of a fascinating cultural object known as the Tibetan prayer wheel. This object (shown in Figure 1, inset) consists of a rotating cylinder, mounted on top of a handle and exists in many sizes. A written prayer is placed inside the chamber and it is traditionally believed that each rotation of the chamber corresponds to a recitation of the prayer. The object affords a special kind of ‘movability’, namely the possibility to produce a circular movement with an object that has a centrifugal force acting upon it. This movement can be experienced as a graceful and meditative repetitive action. The use of the prayer wheel translates an act of faith and intention into a performative action. When undertaken in public, the prayer wheel creates a moment and space for potential inspiration and reaffirmation for both the actor and the observers.

Development & Fabrication: *Synchrum* (shown in Figure 1) is a tangible interface for audience participation in digital performances (Hamidi et al., 2012) inspired by the described characteristics. We employed Maker methods to develop the first prototype and repurposed existing kitchen objects, such as an empty yogurt container for the object chassis, a wooden and metal potato masher for a handle, and a furniture castor with a roller bearing mechanism to provide the experience of a circular and centrifugal force. Small focus group discussions

revealed that the roller-bearing castor afforded a graceful and meditative repetitive action, similar to the prayer wheel. For the second iteration of the prototype, we added a more rigid housing, sensors, a microcontroller, and a wireless communication chip. The electronic components, together, served to detect the rotational speed of the user’s circular movements and to transmit a data stream to a central unit, which would assess emergent states among the various *Synchrum* units (e.g., the degree to which the rotations were synchronized, the distribution of rotational patterns among the units). The central control unit was designed to allow the definition of triggers — a linking of performance output behaviors (e.g., digital audio and video) to certain collective and emergent behaviors among the *Synchrum* units (e.g., a change of state once a certain degree of synchronization has been achieved). Through this, the performance designer can specify changes to take place in the performance (including performance environmental factors), based on the type of input received from the units. The module was designed to allow for the real-time (during performance) tweaking of trigger points. This design decision, along with several others, was informed from our engaged experience as performers and performance designers, and our knowledge of the diversity of audiences in live performances.

We fabricated several copies of the prototype and then arranged for a public performance within which it could be used. During the digital video-based, interactive performance, entitled ‘Liberation’, members of the audience engaged with each other and the performer using their movements. The performance was mounted at two showcase events. The interface was also demoed as an interface to a collaborative musical game for children.

Figure 1. First prototype of *Synchrum* (left) and second prototype (right), with an example of a Tibetan prayer wheel (inset).

Reflection:

Empowerment: We observed the use of Synchron during the performances. The users became engaged with the performance and were observed to engage with the performer and to entrain to one another's movements, confirming our conjecture about the importance of Synchron's performativity and physicality. Synchron allowed a way for the audience members to shift their attention to one another, to interact with each other, in the context of the performance. Through this, Synchron empowered the audience and afforded a process whereby the audience had a say in what happens on stage and in an augmented environment. The audience does not have to be silent, motionless, and passive but can participate and collaborate with each other and the performance.

Our Digital Tapestry

Project: How might a traditional form of collaborative poetry be instantiated using a digital platform, to bring together geographically distributed collaborators? Does Facebook provide a sufficient level of trust, as needed by participants to engage in poetry performance?

Discovery: Collaborative poetry is a style of poetry in which poets collaborate to write a poem together. The tradition of collaborative poetry has existed in many cultures from ancient times to today (Duhamel et al., 2007) (Keene, 1995). It is an art form in which, oftentimes, the artist is both audience and performer.

Development & Fabrication: We developed a project entitled *Our Digital Tapestry* to explore the ideas of collaborative poetry (Hamidi and Baljko, 2012). The work is intended to be a provocation. We decided to simply repurpose an extant social media platform, Facebook. We chose Facebook because of its already established popularity (hence, providing an existing group of artists in the first author's friend community) and its ability to connect people over long distances. By simply redefining the status field of the profile, the page was turned into a virtual stage.

Again, our first-hand experience as performers and artists informed many decisions in the design of the project. For example, we knew that performing with others requires a strong sense of trust, and is encouraged by being aware and interacting with an audience. Hence, we decided to host the project on the first author's Facebook homepage where only his friends and associates could view the artwork-in-progress. In order to address the factor of trust and vulnerability, we decided to restrict participation to only those who knew the first author first-hand and had become friends on the social network previously.

A longitudinal activity was designed wherein a Facebook page was 'seeded' with an opening segment and would be left open for four weeks. The opportunity was then given for collaborators to post subsequent segments, possibly responsive to the most immediate or earlier segments. The poem, thus, developed segment by segment, over time.

Reflection: Over four weeks, nineteen poets from five different countries contributed to a multilingual multimedia poem.

Repurposing: We felt that this project demonstrates the key idea of reuse. We refrained from unnecessarily developing new code and simply redeployed an existing technology in a novel application. In this case, technologically, nothing novel was created: no prototypes were made, nor were any codes written. The only novel element was a change in perspective and the reuse of an existing platform.

Empowerment: Previous research has shown that the lack of social and physical status cues can foster relationships that transcend offline social barriers (Wellman, 1996). Many of the collaborators expressed their preference for performing poetry online rather than in person and mentioned that they found this kind of mediated collaboration less intimidating. The project also, clearly, shows the potential of social networks to facilitate collaboration that transcends geographical and cultural barriers. Many of the poets were from the Middle East, where it is very difficult to have access to an international audience, let alone collaborators, and there are many social and political controls in place that can limit expression and performance opportunities. By bringing the artistic dialogue to a virtual space, the project was able to transcend authority and subvert existing hierarchies and boundaries.

Rafiqh

Project: How can speech interventions be initiated and deployed in a more timely fashion? Once a speech intervention is indicated, how can it be deployed more effectively? How might highly repetitive and boring speech exercises be made more appealing for children?

Discovery: Clinical speech interventions can alleviate or even eliminate different speech disorders in children, but they ideally should be deployed early and intensively. There are a number of barriers, however, both in identifying when intervention should be deployed and in how the intervention is deployed. In terms of early deployment, delays often occur due to bottlenecks in the screening process. The process requires a high degree of clinical specialist involvement, by the Speech Language Pathologist (SLP), in one or more one-on-one sessions, during which natural speech from the child must be elicited. The elicitation of natural speech from small children in a clinical setting takes time and requires a relationship to be established with the child. In terms of how the intervention is deployed, barriers often arise because it can be challenging for a family to undertake the at-home exercises that are a component of an intense intervention. We undertook a number of interviews with SLPs, which revealed that many children, otherwise unmotivated to perform at-home exercises, are highly motivated to use their speech in the context of games in which tangible toys and video and audio prompts were used.

Development & Fabrication: We identified that the opportunity that a SLP could effectively perform screening using recorded speech samples, provided the samples were elicited

Figure 2. Rafigh interface consists of an iPad connected to a living mushroom colony. The three images show the mushroom at different stages of growth

appropriately. We also identified the opportunity to develop digital interactive toys and games to support at-home speech therapy exercises. Whereas previous attempts at this have failed due to shortcomings in speech recognizer technologies, our insight was that the inducement and feedback components of the engagement could be abstracted away from each other. We decided to focus our development efforts on a digital toy that would simply engage a child's speech (rather than try to analyze it and provide feedback). It would simply record speech samples, to be reviewed by an SLP at a subsequent opportunity. We called the toy *Rafigh* (the word for 'companion' in Persian), a digital, interactive toy to aid with speech elicitation and evaluation (Hamidi & Baljko, 2014). Figure 2 shows *Rafigh*.

We decided to use a mushroom colony (Back to the Roots Company, 2009) as a component in the toy. We were inspired to incorporate a living interface for *Rafigh* on the basis of our observations of children's engagement and fascination with living things. The mushroom colony grows considerably within ten to twelve days. We chose this particular product because of the relative short growth cycle of the mushrooms and the potential for manipulating the colony growth rate via control of the amount of water administered. The toy was augmented with electronic components to implement a conditional watering mechanism (e.g., that would be activated when the child responds to SLP-defined prompts from the toy). Other components were added, such as a bubble blower-machine and video display, which could provide other forms of feedback. Speech samples from the interaction are collected and monitored by the SLP at a later time. We use the Arduino microcontroller (Igoe, 2011) to control the actuators in the toy and use the CMU Sphinx open-source speech recognition engine to detect speech (Lamere et al., 2003). *Rafigh* does not attempt to automatically analyze speech; rather, it is responsive to speech and engages the child in a dialogue with the mushrooms.

The first prototype of *Rafigh* engages the child in the caring of a mushroom colony. In our pilot studies, the toy effectively elicited the child 'speaking' with the mushrooms.

Reflection:

Repurposing: The mushroom colony acts as a living slow-media feedback display that responds to input speech. Our approach involves remixing existing technology to create a new digital design. Many of the components are open-source and/or are inexpensive.

Empowerment: *Rafigh* provides an opportunity for the user to care for a living being. Many toys and computer games such as Tamagotchi (Bandai Co. Ltd., Japan, 1996), and Nintendogs (Nintendo Co. Ltd., Japan, 2005) have engaged children in interacting with virtual pets. Research shows that engaging real rather than simulated pets and plants can be beneficial to both parties (Lamers & van Eck, 2012; Isai & Viller, 2010). We aim to empower children and give them responsibility and control over a living interface. We believe that caring for a living being will be a meaningful and enjoyable activity for children and will motivate them to practice and use their speech. Previous research has shown that interacting with pets and plants can have many benefits for children (Levinson, 1980; Bergesen, 1989). Further, regularly attending and taking care of a pet fits in well with a child's daily routine and can provide repeated enforcement with potential benefits for speech practice (Pollak et al., 2010).

DISCUSSION

In recent years, access to rapid prototyping methods, such as 3D printers and open-source hardware platforms, has lowered barriers to the design and production of digital artifacts. In an academic lab setting, we have benefited from these technologies for their power in early prototyping, and for their power as teaching tools in Human-Computer Interaction. This phenomenon, for us, has also triggered a re-examination of the role and responsibility of the HCI researcher. Each new technological tool and technique, from small microcontrollers to virtual worlds, serves to increase the repertoire of digital media with which individuals can create novel interactive objects. These new developments oftentimes reduce or elimi-

nate barriers to use (knowledge barriers and cost barriers, as these tools become more user-friendly and cheaper to source). These expanded/elaborated roles (Designer, HCI researcher, DIY maker) also serve to expand the slate of activity that might be broadly construed as *design*. Sometimes, renaming or de-contextualizing an existing technology is enough to transform it into a new entity and for it to afford new interaction opportunities. This, in turn, serves to rearrange and retrofit of extant knowledge among community members. Given all of this, the question we face now is not whether something *can* be made, but rather *why* should it be made (Ries, 2011). In our examples above, we shifted from a solution-oriented approach to one that finds significance and meaning in designs that support and encourage specific values. This approach emphasized the role of ethical and aesthetic choices, in addition to functional ones. We have drawn upon historical cultural artifacts as sources of inspiration. In the examples above, a key component was involving the community of the user, as motivated by our belief that there is valuable knowledge latent in a user's community.

Subversion, as instantiated in a digital interaction, can afford the user within his or her community and context an opportunity for empowerment. One way to accomplish this is by encouraging and actualizing social practices, such as collaboration, democratization, and creative expression, via interactive activities that are mediated by digital media. However, the relative value of various social practices has its basis in culture. Extant cultural artifacts can be an effective way to identify such social values and be inspired by them. These artifacts, which are simply the 'technologies' of a prior time, reveal values that may be relevant to current, digital design contexts when seen through the lens of cultural anthropology. The re-imagination of existing technology, as inspired by historical cultural artifacts, is only natural as these artifacts are the ancestors of digital designs. Two different, yet complementary, veins of activity inspire our approach. In one vein are the approaches informed by critical technical practices, such as Reflective Design (Sengers et al., 2005), and Thoughtful Interaction Design (Löwgren & Stolterman, 2004) that advocates the application of critical theory and reflection to design. In the other vein are the Hacker-Maker approaches, with their emphases on sharing, challenge to authority, and playful cleverness.

SUMMARY & CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have discussed subversion and empowerment, drawing across disciplinary boundaries (Design, Human-Computer Interaction, and the Maker Movement). Our aim is to draw into focus the following three aspects of design: (i) looking to cultural artifacts for inspiration, (ii) fabrication approaches that emphasize repurposing and rearrangement of technologies, and (iii) critical reflection. Cultural artifacts afford a point of inquiry into the sources of latent knowledge from the user and their community, and to incorporate engaged knowledge arising from contexts of use and underlying social processes. The Maker and Hacking communities have shifted beyond amateur expertise and offer techniques for the

reimagining and rearrangement of extant technologies. Finally, critical reflection is necessary in the examination of how interactive digital media affords interactions that question, challenge, and transform extant prevalent social dynamics.

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LEARNING ADVANCED FINNISH: EXPLORATIONS FOR SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION

Tania Rodriguez-Kaarto

Aalto School of Arts, Design and Architecture (ARTS), Helsinki Finland

✉ tania.rodriguez.garcia@aalto.fi

Young-Ae Hahn

Yonsei University in Wonju, South Korea

✉ yahahn@yonsei.ac.kr

ABSTRACT

The Finnish government offers various educational programs to aid immigrants — currently 5.2 % of the population — in language acquisition and cultural assimilation, but the efficiency of these programs in improving high-skilled immigrants' job opportunities has been questioned. This study uncovers what impedes the high-skilled immigrants' transition from intermediate level to advanced level language skills, and explores future instructional design solutions, with a qualitative study including textbook authors, instructors, and learners.

Findings report that current teaching materials with too heavy emphasis on grammar, and instructors' too strict teaching styles overrule what intermediate level learners need the most: comprehensible/communicative input optimal to the learner's current level, professional vocabulary, practical conversation skills, and cultural knowledge. For this, we suggest new approaches: teaching materials with low cognitive loads and effective visual design, adaptive-interactive text for personalized comprehension lessons, participatory storytelling platforms for personalized topics, and involving the whole community as a learning environment for more practice opportunities.

KEYWORDS: *Second-language acquisition, instructional-design, visual-communication design, professional language improvement, design for social integration*

INTRODUCTION

Immigration has been on the rise in Finland during the past two decades. As stated by Ikäläinen (2003, cited in Miettinen & Puurunen, 2007), upon their arrival, immigrants of all types (highly- and low-skilled) are expected to 'integrate themselves' into Finnish society. However, 'unemployment rate of immigrants is three times that of the majority population' (Ministry of Employment and Economy in Finland, 2012, p.1), and 'a high level of education does not protect foreign-background residents from unemployment as efficiently as it does the domestic population' (Statistics, 2013, p.24). The Finnish *Act on the Integration of Immigrants and Reception of Asylum Seeker* (Ministry of Employment and Economy in Finland, 1999-2009) aims to provide immigrants with protection and guaranteed participation in society, by bettering the chances for immigrants to find job opportunities and emotional well-being; these programs include Finnish language instruction.

Nevertheless, the language programs only comprise of basic level lessons, without covering Finnish for highly-skilled professional activities. Also, educated immigrants are expected

to manage social codes proper to their fields, because 'It is more than just degree, language skills or social relationships. [...] mastering the social code, [...] where a person assimilates into the society and society's requisites *the right way*' (Kyhä, 2011, p.65). Assimilation courses, however, do not provide sufficient education on Finnish cultural and communication patterns either. The stages of government integration programs, and the immigrant's steps towards finding employment and bettering their language skills is illustrated in Figure 1.

As a result, ironically, more educated immigrants find it harder to find the right positions where they can fulfill their professional goals and be assimilated into Finnish society. In this study, high-skilled immigrants are defined as immigrants with Bachelor degrees, or higher levels of education, following Iredale's definition (2001, cited in Cerna, 2010). Recent media coverage has shown that unemployment rates are high among high-skilled immigrants (Yleisradio, 2010). Foreign health-care workers found that the language, among other factors, force them to leave (Yleisradio, 2013). The increasing number of jobless immigrants can cause social costs and unrest in the future.

Figure 1. Outline of integration program in stages and stakeholders

In light of the situation, this research explores efficacies of current Finnish language education methods and materials, and approaches future directions of instructional design interventions for intermediate level Finnish learners, in order for them to acquire the necessary linguistic skills for professional activities. Two research questions were posed:

Q1. What are the limitations of current language courses that prevent intermediate level Finnish learners from building more advanced, professional level language skills?

Q2. What makes current teaching methods/materials effective? From the lessons, which directions of design interventions are conceivable, to strengthen high-skilled immigrants' job competency?

In order to answer these questions, the team has looked into previous studies about the impact of emotions in learning (Gundogan & Erbug, 2006; Tung & Deng, 2004), and current theories of second language acquisition with an emphasis on effective language teaching/learning methods in the next

section, then details of our research activities in the Research Design and key findings in the Discussion section that follows, with future design implications in the Conclusions.

THEORIES OF ADULT SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION

How can a second language be effectively learnt or taught? Krashen (1981; 1982) proposed five hypotheses on the subject. First, the acquisition and learning of a language differ in that acquisition is ‘the way children develop ability in their first language’, while ‘using the language for communication’ is implicit, informal, and natural ways. Language learning, on the other hand, is gaining ‘conscious knowledge of a second language, knowing the rules’ in the forms of ‘formal knowledge’ (Krashen, 1982, p.10). An adult learner can both *acquire* and *learn* a new language. Second, the monitor hypothesis (Krashen, 1982, pp.15-19) suggests that the use of Monitor (i.e., the formal knowledge of language) can be either overused or underused, but the *optimal Monitor users* use grammatical knowledge appropriately and it does not interfere with their communication.

Third, the natural order hypothesis maintains that ‘the acquisition of grammatical structures proceeds in a predictable order’ (pp.12-13), such as learning progressive verbs precedes learning regular past verbs and possessive forms. Then, how can a learner advance from one level to the next in language acquisition, as opposed to learning? With the fourth, input hypothesis, referring a learner’s current developmental stage i , Krashen posits that ‘the acquirer understands input that contains $i + 1$, [...] focus[ing] on the meaning and not the form of the message’ (Krashen, 1982, pp.20-21). By relying on context, knowledge of the world, and other extra-linguistic information, a learner can understand a new sentence structure. Lastly, the affective filter hypothesis shows the learner as a person with affective variables, such as motivation, self-confidence, or anxiety that either encourage or discourage the learner to seek more acquisition opportunities (Krashen, 1982, p.31).

Based on the hypotheses, Krashen (1982, pp.63-76) recommends providing the following for effective language acquisition in either a formal or informal learning environment:

- Comprehensible input with simple codes — simple and short sentences, articulated pronunciation, repetition of common vocabulary, etc. — which is a bit beyond the learner’s current level ($i + 1$).
- Non-linguistic means of comprehension such as showing objects and pictures, in order to take advantage of the student’s knowledge of the world as part of the lesson.
- Meaningful communicative input where i (current level) + 1 is naturally supplied, not by mechanical grammatical drills, to make lessons practical.
- Lessons that do not put students on the defensive with too much error correction or forced production, so students remain open to input.

- Input that is sufficient in quantity, to make sure $i + 1$ is repeatedly provided in diverse forms, and enough time for students to build competency before speaking.

We found that some of Krashen’s recommendations were already put to use in the Finnish teachers’ classes interviewed for this study, but different approaches/emphases were observed from their teaching methods and materials as well. In the next section, the findings from a qualitative study with Finnish teachers and learners continues.

RESEARCH DESIGN

In order to investigate the research questions — the limitations of current language courses for intermediate level learners, and the future directions of design interventions — the research team carried out (i) email interviews with the authors of popular Finnish textbooks, (ii) interviews with three instructors, and (iii) interviews with five intermediate-level Finnish learners.

Task one: Email interviews with authors of Finnish teaching materials

Teaching/learning materials (textbooks, etc.) are most relevant to the learner’s in- and out-of-class experiences. They provide both linguistic and non-linguistic information; visual features in the textbook, such as images depicting objects, enhance learning as linkages between the learner’s knowledge of the world and language lessons (Krashen, 1982, pp.63-76).

For these reasons, in response to the two research questions, the kick-start of this study was a review of the eleven Finnish textbooks available in assimilation courses. In order to learn more about them, a brief email questionnaire was sent to the authors, with questions on the historical context of authoring, the author’s teaching background, their perspectives on the language courses’ role in foreigners’ assimilation, and the author’s opinions/involvement in the visual design process. The authors of *Harjoituskirja Suomen Kielen Alkeisoppikirja* [Workbook: Basics of Finnish Language], *Kuulostaa Hyvältä* [Sounds Good] and *Sairaan Hyvää Suomea* [Insanely good Finnish] responded.

All authors have years of teaching experience, and wrote their books for their own classes. They all acknowledged the importance of the visual design of textbooks in enhancing learning experience. *Harjoituskirja Suomen Kielen Alkeisoppikirja* [Workbook: Basics of Finnish Language], was written for university students in 1987, with heavy emphasis on grammar. It has been reprinted for decades, with only minor changes in content over time, to make it up-to-date (e.g., exchanging a record player for iPod, or a restaurant for a night club). *Kuulostaa Hyvältä* [Sounds Good] focuses on the conversational use of the language. From the authors of *Hyvin Mene!* [It’s going good] and *Suomen Mestari 1* [Finnish Master 1], we did not get any responses. Later, during interviews with teachers, we learned they were written in response to the *National Core*

Curriculum for Integration Training for Adult Immigrants announced in 2012. These two books were written for a broad range of learners, both skilled and unskilled immigrants, from K-12 to college level classes. In these books, a noticeably different design approach — color-coding, less saturated pages, and clear visual hierarchy — makes the content structure accessible for the learner. Unlike other books, *Sairaan hyvää Suomea* [Insanely good Finnish] was written specifically for foreign students in the field of nursery, to assist their professional language acquisition. A comparison of five much used books — *Kieli Käyttöön-Suomen Kielen Alkeisoppikirja*, *Harjoituskirja Suomen Kielen Alkeisoppikirja*, *Hyvin Menee!*, *Suomen Mestari 1*, and *Sairaan Hyvää Suomea* — is presented in Figure 2.

Task two: Instructor interviews

Secondly, in order to learn more about the effectiveness of current teaching methods and materials in language courses, we interviewed three Finnish teachers. The interviews lasted on average 45-50 minutes, and were conducted at the teachers' work places. For the anonymity of the participants, we refer to them as Male Teacher 1 (MT1), Female Teacher 1 (FT1), and Female Teacher 2 (FT2). MT1 and FT1 are native Finnish speakers,

while FT2 is a Peruvian Finnish speaker. MT1 and FT1 work with a wide range of learners, from university students to refugees. FT2 works with international and Finnish students in the field of health services and nursing. The instructors have teaching experiences that range between eight to fifteen years.

For our first research question, the interviews uncovered what prevents intermediate Finnish language learners from advancing. In relation to the second research question, we enquired about the teachers' opinions on the visual design and content of teaching materials, their ideas for the ideal teaching environment, and their methods and materials in order to get their suggestions for improvements.

Task three: Student interviews

We interviewed five intermediate level Spanish-speaking Finnish learners who have lived at least seven years in Finland, and have obtained post-graduate degrees from Finnish institutions; they were a sample of highly-skilled immigrants whose language needs this study intends to explore.

The student interviews lasted on average 45-50 minutes and were conducted on school grounds or work places. For anonymity, the participants were referred to as Female Student

TITLE	<i>Kieli Käyttöön, Suomen Kielen Alkeisoppikirja</i> [Basics of Finnish Language"]	<i>Harjoituskirja. Suomen kielen Alkeisoppikirja</i> [Translation]	<i>Hyvin Menee!</i> [It's going good]	<i>Suomen Mestari 1</i> [Finnish Master]	<i>Sairaan Hyvää Suomea</i> [Insanely Good Finnish]
FIRST EDITION	1997-2012	1987-2011	2002- 2012	2010-2012	2010-2011
TARGET USER	University student	University student	University and lower degree student	University and lower degree student	Nursing-major university student
PURPOSE	Classroom teaching	Classroom teaching	Classroom teaching/ Self-study	Classroom teaching/ Self-study	Classroom teaching / Self-study
TOPIC	General topics	General topics	General topics	General topics	Professional nursing language in Finnish
LEARNING EMPHASIS	• Basic and mid-level grammar instruction, vocabulary and an introductory level of Finnish culture information	• Basic grammar instruction	• Basic grammar instruction and cultural lessons	• Basic grammar instruction and cultural lessons	• Vocabulary - specialized in the teaching of nursing skills and techniques in Finnish language

Figure 2. Most frequently used Finnish textbooks, compared in terms of publication year, target user, purpose, topic, and learning emphasis.

one (FS1), Female Student two (FS2), Male Student one (MS1), Male Student two (MS2) and Male Student three (MS3). They all belong to different fields and their work situations were somewhat variable: MS1 and MS2 hold academic positions but use English at work. MS3 has a position in an IT company where English is spoken. FS1 is self-employed, and FS2 is unemployed.

During the student interviews, their opinion on the courses, instructor competency, materials, and especially the visual design of textbooks were questioned. Students also made suggestions on how to improve language courses, along with their idea of an ideal learning environment. Details of their comments are analyzed in the next section.

DISCUSSION

In this section, insights gained from student and teacher interviews about language courses and use of teaching materials are discussed from two aspects: (i) the limitations of current instruction methods and the context/environment in which the learning takes place, in teaching advanced levels of Finnish specific to professional fields, and (ii) the efficacy of current teaching materials, that point to directions of feasible design proposals.

Challenges in current Finnish teaching methods and learning environment

The Finnish language, which belongs to Uralic language family, is not connected to Germanic or Latin linguistic groups, so the initial stages of Finnish learning can be very demanding, due to the amount of vocabulary and grammatical rules to acquire. According to a news article ('Finnish among most difficult', 2013, pp.2-7), it takes '44 weeks or 1100 hours' of active learning for an English speaker to achieve a level of written and oral skill sufficient to work with the language. Its fifteen grammatical cases or 'noun conjugations and prepositions of place can be a puzzler' to the learner ('Why Finnish can seem like', 2013, para. 4). In addition to that, the following problems were mentioned during the student interview.

Lack of comprehensible/communicative input in an immersive learning environment

Language learners in early stages need comprehensible input with simple codes of information a bit beyond the learner's current level, in order for him/her to access the next level of linguistic skills (Krashen, 1982, pp.63-76). Studying in an immersive environment allows the learner to be exposed to a large quantity of natural, meaningful input, with enough practicing opportunities. Learning Finnish in Helsinki, however, does not always provide such advantages, according to student interviewees in this study.

First, instructors do not provide meaningful comprehensible/communicative input during the class, because they would rather use the limited time for repetitive grammar exercises

— from the instructor's point of view, the grammar drills are necessities. Instead, instructors encourage students to use the language in any given occasions outside the classroom. Nevertheless, students' real-world interactions with Finns are not necessarily helpful, comprehensive input. In such situations, the conversational skills needed are much higher than what the learners can handle, and they do not get proper feedback from Finns, so the same mistakes will be repeated. Many learners will walk away from the situations feeling confused and frustrated.

Second, less motivated learners tend to think that learning Finnish is not necessary, because Finns are fluent in English and are ready to speak if needed. It is the most popular foreign language in Finnish ground schools ('More Finnish kids opt to study English', 2013). Surrounded by them, some learners are not motivated to use Finnish as often as they should be, and they begin to overlook the need to be proficient.

In-class teaching methods and styles

The learner's first encounter with Finnish language is from language course instructors; their roles and the methods employed in the class are of high relevance to the learners' advancement. About their classroom experience, many participants commented on the teachers' unenergetic style of teaching or being too keen on correcting the student to the point of frustrating them.

We had turns to answer, and for me to say double *tt*'s and double *pp*'s is a hassle and so when we had exams or give answers I didn't pronounce well or didn't make the sentences perfect. She insisted to make sentences perfect, I was very frustrated because it was very difficult (MS4, from personal communication, October 4, 2013).

Student interviewees also commented on courses that are not structured with the right comprehensive level of input. Such classes can turn into negative experiences as the next example shows; a teacher set the pace for the most skilled in the classroom, and it was way beyond $i + 1$ input for other students who were left behind.

The teacher assumed that we were very fluent and I wasn't, but the people around me were, so she was speaking so fast everything in the class was 100 km/h for me and (...) it was a very embarrassing experience for me (MS4, from personal communication, October 4, 2013).

When teachers manage to create a good environment in the class, to engage students with diverse and interesting activities, providing the input proper to their level, then the learners' frustration and bad experiences can be prevented.

An analysis of teaching material

During the interview, students and teachers discussed both problematic and effective aspects of learning materials, around visual design, content, and images. Their comments provided useful insights on future design interventions for an improved learning experience.

Visual clarity

In this study, student interviewees understood visual clarity as design with less cognitive load, ease of use/read, and content relevance. The learner's cognitive load can be reduced with an optimal amount of content per page. The *rhetorical clusters* (Schriver, 1997) in the page layout make it easier to use/read the book. Lastly, graphic elements and typographic treatment can highlight a specific part of a text or a word in order to show key learning points to focus on.

Cognitive load In relation to the amount of content in each section/page, the discussion with teachers showed that they prefer a book with enough content for the student to study on his/her own, and also to leave some room for extra input from the teacher for a lively classroom experience. For this reason, they favored simple images, which make it easier to give further input and create discussions.

Effort on clarity, partly based on the fact that they give as little info as possible [...] is easier to add things to a description that is simplified, than to try to figure out things from the complicated description (FT2, from personal communication, October 11th, 2013).

Student participants also mentioned the information overload coming from visual saturation that hinders the formation of clear content clusters, and the learner's concentration on one topic at a time. They favored some textbooks with unsaturated layouts and supporting visual elements like images, color coding, and typographic variations that make key learning points prominent (Figure 3).

Ease of use Participants also mentioned how some visual features of the books allow them to recognize how the content is structured on each page, and over the entire length of the book. First, on each page, effective layouts create *rhetorical clusters*, i.e., 'a group of text elements designed to work together as a functional unit within a document [...] help the reader interpret the content in a certain way' (Schriver, 1997, p.343, cited in Gillenson, 2008), formed following Gestalt principles of organization, such as proximity grouping, and continuity (Koffka, 1935; Köhler, 1929).

Second, for the whole book, consistent visual styles for elements are perceived as visual references, and allow the learners to perceive the book as a structured whole. The chapter and section titles differentiated with typography styles help students recognize content hierarchy. The consistency of color-coding supports learners in information spotting. Graphic symbols indicating different types of content were also considered to enhance browsability and make it easier to remember where content is placed in the book (Figure 4).

That's what I meant with the reference, it is easy to mark and then to go back to it. The browsability is quite good because every page is different and not packed with text, it makes it easy to browse and find what you're looking for (SF2, from personal communication, 23 September, 2013).

Content relevance Lastly, interviewees commented on how visual design features support acquiring various key learning

points. Graphic organizers, such as charts or tables, were favored because they provide summarized core information (Figure 3 and 5).

Many participants also mentioned key learning points emphasized with typographic treatments; for example, the grammar inflection section of *Suomen Mestari 1* (Figure 5) was made digestible with variations in type and color on the word endings (vowels—'ä' change to 'o', etc.).

You have the color [...] where you have the endings and when you have double letters so you really concentrate [...] If you write everything in the same color you don't have this understanding or you have to memorize [...] (FS1, from personal communication, September 20th, 2013).

In short, the visual clarity of teaching materials can enhance the learner's experience. Their cognitive load can be reduced with the optimal amount of content. Textbooks will be easier to use, with formation of rhetorical clusters and consistent use of color and type variations to make clear to the learner the content hierarchies. Finally, graphic organizers and visual treatments can help the learner by summarizing information of a chapter or highlighting key learning points. More suggestions for future design directions continue in the Conclusions section.

Content

During the interviews, the content of language books was discussed, with the purpose of learning how the current content scaffolds for acquisition advanced levels of professional language and cultural knowledge.

Most books turned out to be focusing on grammar and vocabulary building for basic and intermediate level courses (Figure 1). Some are targeted to university students and others to lower levels. Some are better fits for beginners and can be studied by the student alone, while others are for intermediate level students, designed to be used along with the teacher's guidance.

In regards to textbook content, instructors feel that the content is appropriate for beginners, regardless of the presentation (overall visual design) of the books. They feel that Finnish contemporary customs and cultural information is missing in them; the teacher should provide it as extra input in the class. Meanwhile, in regards to the same textbooks, students pointed out the lack of (i) relevance to their professional fields and required vocabulary, (ii) practicality, since many examples do not reflect the daily use of the language, and (iii) insights on contemporary customs and cultural information (e.g., Finn's idea of privacy or their communication styles) that they could not learn either from textbooks or from teachers, according to students' comments.

First, regarding the relevance of textbook topics to their professions, student interviewees commented that the books focus on generic use of language and none of them are targeted to their professional fields. In this study, all student interviewees hold postgraduate degrees in various fields, and some

2 Kuuntele ja kirjoita palkannimet vihkoon.

3 Kysy multa opiskelijoita heidän nimesään ja miten se kirjoitetaan. Kirjoita nimet vihkoon.

Numerot	
0	nolla
1	yksi
2	kaksi
3	kolme
4	neljä
5	viisi
6	kuusi
7	seitsemän
8	kahdeksan
9	yhdeksän
10	kymmenen
11	yksitoista
12	kaksoista
13	kolmetoista
14	neljätoista
15	viisitoista
16	kuusitoista
17	seitsemäntoista
18	kahdeksantoista
19	yhdeksäntoista
20	kaksikymmentä
21	kaksikymmentäyksi
22	kaksikymmentäkaksi
23	kaksikymmentäkolme
24	kaksikymmentäneljä
25	kaksikymmentäviisi
30	kolmekymmentä
40	neljäkymmentä
50	viisikymmentä
60	kuusikymmentä
70	seitsemänkymmentä
80	kahdeksänkymmentä
90	yhdeksänkymmentä
100	sata
101	satayksi
200	kaksisataa
300	kolmesataa
1 000	tuhat
10 000	kymmentuhatta
100 000	satatuhatta
1 000 000	miljoona

HUOMAA!
1/2 puoli
1 1/2 puoliosta
2-3 pari
3-5 muutama

4 Kuuntele ja toista numerot.

5 Kuuntele ja kirjoita numerot vihkoon.

6 Kirjoita kysymykset tai numerot.

Kuinka monta? - Viisi.
Montako? - Viisi.

1. Kuinka monta?

2. Montako?

3. _____ ? - Seitsemän.

4. _____ ? - Seitsemän.

Figure 3. Example from Hyvin Menee! [It's going good!] of low cognitive load: adequate amount of content surrounded by sufficient white spaces; graphic elements that suggest type of exercise and type variations.

5 Kuuntele radiohaastattelu ja kirjoita, mitä nämä henkilöt ostavat:

- Virpi Saarela _____
- Lasse Nyman _____
- Jaana Mattila _____
- Jaakko ja Mikaela _____

6 Olet kahvilassa.

Katso oheista listaa. Tee parisi kanssa keskustelu siitä, mitä haluat syödä (tilata).

Ruokalista	
Kahvi	1,70 €
Espresso	2,30 €
Latte	2,70 €
Capuccino	2,70 €
Tee	1,50 €
Haudutettu tee	2,50 €
Kaakao	3,00 €
Limsa	2,80 €
Appelsiinimehu	2,50 €
Pulla	2,30 €
Marjapiirakka	3,00 €
Muffini	2,70 €
Porkkanakakku	2,70 €
Sämpylät	
Juustosämpylä	3,00 €
Kinkkusämpylä	3,00 €
Karjalanpiirakka	2,50 €
Ciabatta	3,50 €

Kirjoita, mitä sinulla on keittiössä. Kirjoita myös, mitä sinulla ei ole keittiössä.

Malli:

Minun keittiöni
Minulla on vedenkeitin, mutta minulla ei ole leivinpäääntä. Minulla on ...

Kappaleessa opitaan
• kertomaan, mitä sinusta tuntuu

Mattia ja Jannea jännittää

Matti Kukkola ja Janne Lahtela ovat jääkiekkokatsomossa. He katsovat jääkiekko-ottelua. Peli on jännittävä, koska sen voittaja on uusi Suomen mestari. Katsomossa on kylmä. Mattia ja Jannea päälle, vaikka heillä on paljon vaatteita päällä. On toinen erä, ja numerot ovat 2-1 kotijoukkueen hyväksi.

- Katso, miten Miettinen takkaa koko ajan meidän Peltola! Eikä tuomari tee mitään! Minua sitten raivostuttaa tuollainen tuomari, Matti sanoo.

- Niin, tuomari ei huomaa tässä pelissä juuri mitään. Ihme, että kotijoukkue on vielä johdossa. Mutta kyllä meidänkin pelaajat osavat pelata rumasti. Minua suuttuttaa se, että urheilui ei nykyisin enää ole reilua. Joskus tuntuu siltä, että mitä enemmän väkivaltaa, sen parempi. Minä inhoan väkivaltaa. Ojoi, nyt oli maali lähellä, Janne huutaa.

- No niin oli. Minua huolestuttaa se, että meidän joukkue häviää tämän matsin, Matti sanoo.

- Niin. Nyt on sitten erätauko. Haetaanko kaakaota? Se lämmitää meitä ainakin vähän, Janne ehdottaa.

- Joo, haetaan vaan, Matti sanoo.

Figure 4. Use of visual elements—type variations and color management—enhances browsability and facilitates information spotting for each page and the whole book.

Ainesanat partitiivissa

Mikä on ainesana?

- ruoka ja juoma: salaatti, riisi, tee, vesi...
- materiaalit: ilma, metalli, hiekka, puu...
- abstraktit sanat: rakkaus, ystävyys, kauneus, energia...

1. Lauseen loppu: ainesana on partitiivissa

Tämä on kahvia. Tämä on spagettia.
Kupissa on kahvia. Lautasella on spagettia.
Juon kahvia. Me syömme spagettia.

2. Lauseen alku: ainesana ei partitiivissa

Kahvi on kupissa.
Spagetti on kotoisin Italiasta.

3. Ainesana + on + adjektiivi partitiivissa

Kahvi on kuumaa.
Spagetti on hyvää.
Rakkaus on kaunista.

HUOM! Kirja on hyvä. (Kirja ei ole ainesana.)

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Partitiivin monikko

ja/jä

o, ö, u, y

juusto	juustoja
tyttö	tyttöjä
kurkkü	kurkkuja
hylly	hyllyjä

i->i-sanat

tomaatti	tomaatteja
keksi	keksejä

a

pizza	pizzoja
kala	kaloja

(jos 1. tavussa on a, e tai i)

ia/iä

a, ä, i

muna	munia
leipä	leipiä
pieni	pieniä

nen-sanat

herkullise-	herkullisia
hampurilaise-	hampurilaisia

ita/itä

e

herne	herneitä
tuore	tuoreita

2 vokaalia

jää	jäitä
suklaa	suklaita

ka/kä

mansikka	mansikoita
----------	------------

la/lä

sämpylä	sämpyloita
---------	------------

na/nä

peruna	perunoita
--------	-----------

ra/rä

makkara	makkaroita
---------	------------

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Figure 5. A spread from Suomen Mestari 1 [Finnish Master 1] with summary tables.

continue to work in the same fields using English language. All of them agreed that, even after achieving an intermediate level of Finnish, they still cannot access mainstream job opportunities due to their insufficient professional language skills in their own fields; they are forced to apply only to positions that accept English as a working language, which are few. One interviewee speculated that textbook authors might not know what the learner needs — ‘they need to know what I want, my purposes, intentions, and my needs’ (FS2, from personal communication, 23rd September, 2013).

The problem is recognized, and some advance level language and communication training opportunities are available in specific professional fields. The research team found learning materials specifically targeted to college level nursing and health-care degrees — *Sairaan Hyvää Suomea* [Insanely good Finnish] by Kela, Korpela and Lehtinen — where students are presented with vocabulary and transcripts of real conversations between nurses and patients. This book teaches, in addition to vocabulary specific to the field, protocols and procedures between workers and patients in Finland. The dialogues reflect the spoken use of the language.

Second, student interviewees wanted content with practicality, such as dialogues that reflect everyday use of the language — idioms, slang and more complex vocabulary — of proficient speakers, to be able to acquire them and feel culturally integrated at their workplaces. Regarding how students feel about

current textbook content, we have selected some insightful quotes from our interviewees discussing the practicality of the material. The following quote points out what topics students may better relate to:

There are some examples of conversations, and they were very short and more close to how conversations are in reality, not this really imaginary situations like going to the bank... you don't go to the bank in Finland anymore (FS2, from personal communication, September 23rd, 2013).

The lack of practicality has been a common discussion among our interviewees; in the textbook, students could not see how the language molds and reshapes in use, which made it hard for them to become active speakers. The other side of this problem is the impracticality of current content. Students talked about the amount of vocabulary they memorized in the beginners level but never used in daily conversations. In some books, introduction of new vocabulary is done (often in large quantities) to represent Finnish culture in actions, objects, and places. Some of this content, however, is presented in a decontextualized manner, with poor visual representations.

Third, current teaching materials do not cover cultural and behavioral knowledge of Finnish culture, while the learners aim to understand Finnish cultural codes as a key part of workplace communication. Being able to understand unspoken forms of communication at workplaces, as well as overcoming

differences in communication styles — e.g., communicating in a direct manner, without extra politeness, is not the norm in Latin cultures where student interviewees are from in this study — is what foreign applicants are expected to know. Teachers, however, seem to be unaware of this need, because the cultural communication patterns might seem too obvious to them.

From the teacher's point of view, teaching the cultural aspect of linguistic communication in the classroom is challenging and ineffective. For example, a teacher from a nursing school regarded some colloquial dialogues in *Sairaan Hyvää Suomea* [Insanely good Finnish] inappropriate, since they could sound disrespectful, even though that is how native Finnish speakers say it. She maintained that the cultural aspect of the language should be taught only in practice, where the learner can observe and clarify the native speaker's language use in the context.

Elderly people don't like to be addressed in spoken colloquial Finnish and you have to ask permission to address them in familiar tone, if you teach nurses to address patients this way it violates the principles of nursery (FT3, from personal communication, October 21st, 2013).

We concluded that (i) there is a need for courses/materials designed to teach language specialized in high-skilled learner's professional fields, with up-to-date and relevant topics. (ii) Practicality is a concern among students since textbook examples are much different from the spoken Finnish. (iii) Cultural communication teaching is missing from textbooks, and not widely addressed by teachers in the class. Learners need this type of knowledge to holistically understand cultural differences that are reflected in the use of language. Our findings point to the need for design solutions that allow learners to construct their own teaching/learning materials. More suggestions for future design directions continue in the Conclusions section.

Images

Among the topics discussed with learners and teachers were the role of images in books and their importance for language learning. Learners pointed to the strengths and weaknesses of illustrations and photographs from books. Most comments about the photographs were positive since they visually describe what is being studied (accuracy/closeness), add complementary information (informational value), in addition to making the learning more engaging.

Accuracy/closeness Some observations were made on the photographs that clarify the meaning of the content at hand. For example, the inclusion of a photo of *korvapuusti*, a typical Finnish bread, was considered to enhance the understanding of the text (Figure 6, left). Many positive comments were made on images of the most common products available in supermarkets (Figure 6, right).

These are exactly the products that you see and I remember the first time I came to Finland and went to the supermarket, I was super lost and it was a pain because I didn't understand even if you see the product, you have to read and I didn't understand (FS2, from personal communication, September 23rd, 2013).

With images, learners became familiar with the products, and remembered the difficulties in understanding labels in the early stages of language learning. Photographs were favored over drawings, as complementary information on the subject was richer with photographs.

Informational value Images or other visual elements such as dialogue boxes can broaden the comprehension of what is being studied with additional information, while too simple or schematic ones lack such strength — they do not enhance nor provide enough additional input to the content. In the following example (Figure 6, left), a brief dialog box accompanied by one image depicts real use of language. It helped recollection of previous experiences and enhanced retention of lessons, in the learners' opinion.

Use of drawings and photographs assist learning difficult concepts, such as prepositions of place in the Finnish language. Figure 7 describes how prepositions (*mihin*, *missä*, *mistä*; where to, where you are, from where) inflect the endings of the following words, depending on whether it is an open or closed space; with the image, students can better relate their previous experiences to the learning points.

In addition to that, according to interviewees, some textbooks were actually fun to read, and they seemed lighter in content, thanks to the use of supporting images. Others were not received well; *Kieli Käyttöön-Suomen Kielen Alkeisoppikirja* [Language Use — Finnish language basic book] was considered un-engaging, due to its extensive use of text, monochromatic and monotonous style of drawings.

In short, regarding the value of images in textbooks, the learners appreciated that they can learn more from some images (mostly photographs) thanks to their accuracy and informational values, but if images are too simplistic, or just decorative — by repeating the same information already presented in the text — they were not considered functional.

CONCLUSIONS

The government integration programs for immigrants provide basics of Finnish language, but the programs do not cover Finnish for specialized professional activities. In consequence, high-skilled immigrants' employment opportunities are reduced, and a long-term unemployment hinders immigrants' assimilation process generating anxiety, stress and depression. This study aimed to uncover (i) why intermediate level Finnish language learners have difficulties in acquiring both specialized languages required for high-skilled professionals and cultural fluency, and (ii) which design solutions are conceivable, inspired by the effective features of current teaching methods/materials.

The findings from this study suggest room for improvement in current Finnish language lessons: lack of practice opportunities while classroom teaching is limited and focused on repetitive grammar drills, and a lack of content relevant to students' professional needs, practicality for daily use, and cultural

Leipätiskillä

Kappaleessa opitaan

- asioimaan kaupassa
- tilaamaan itsepalveluravintolassa
- ruokasanastoa
- partitiivi

Myyjä: Numero 67! Päivää! Mitäs teille saisi olla?
 Asiakas: Päivää. Saanko 2 patonkia ja 5 vaaleaa sämpylää.
 Myyjä: Kiitos. Entä muuta?
 Asiakas: Onko pulla tuoretta?
 Myyjä: Kyllä on, suoraan uunista. Millaista pullaa laitetaan?
 Asiakas: Otan 3 korvapuustia. En voi juoda kahvia ilman tuoretta pullaa.
 Myyjä: Tässä olkaa hyvä.
 Asiakas: Kiitos, hei hei!
 Myyjä: Kiitti, hei hei!

Kalat

Viljatuotteet

Maitotuotteet

Juomat

Muut ruoka-aineet

Figure 6. A page with photos and dialogue boxes enhances students' recollection and retention (left). On the opposite page, images of basic grocery items describe what is being studied (right).

1.2.
MISSÄ? - MISTÄ? - MIHIN? - MINNE?

Hän on kioskillä.

Hän lähtee kioskilta.

Hän menee kioskille.

Figure 7. Place prepositions from *Kieli Käyttöön- suomen kielen alkeisoppikirja*: visual images help the learner understand inflections in word endings, depending on whether the subject: is at-, coming from-, or going to- (the kiosk).

knowledge. The results also include the implications of effective (visual) features of current teaching methods/materials for future design proposals.

First, the whole Community can serve as a learning environment. One suggestion made by an instructor was helping students have more interactions with native speakers, by running daily errands in Finnish, and collecting study credits from it. This idea can be developed into *the whole community as a learning environment* where instructors, students, and Helsinki residents can collaborate in Finnish language education; for example, an intermediate level student can get work-related activities in her field done in Finnish, to collect stamps or grades on her *language study passport* from native speaker professionals.

Second, adaptive-interactive learning materials can be utilized. During the teacher interviews, one instructor showed a series of newspaper articles written in three different versions of complexity in vocabulary and comprehension levels (Figure 8). The articles were useful in teaching students with varied reading-comprehension skills; students can progressively acquire advanced levels of linguistic skills. This idea points to an adaptive language teaching system which generates/presents the same material in different versions of difficulties, to provide customized comprehensive input for learners.

Figure 8. An adaptive reading material for students with varied reading-comprehension skills, developed by a teacher

Lastly, an online, participatory storytelling platform can be used to collect up-to-date and personalized topics of text for the learner, in order to make language lessons more relevant to their interests and levels. During a student interview, the idea of studying with real-world events/activities, instead of practicing imaginary dialogues, as in current textbooks, emerged, which is not possible/feasible with printed textbooks. Online tools where instructors, the community of Finnish native speakers, and students can collaboratively compose customized teaching materials will meet the learners' diverse needs. Participants can share articles, build vocabulary, and utilize different types of media for a more engaging learning experience. This platform can also let Finns share their observations and reflections on various issues, to help foreigners understand Finnish culture in a holistic way.

The authors expect the solutions will address the learner's study progress, as well as their emotional benefits, because the solutions will reduce their stress and frustration with personalized materials and more interesting/useful content.

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THE ORAL PATRIMONY OF A COMMUNITY IN THE CONSTRUCTION OF CREATIVE AND CULTURAL INDUSTRIES: A STRATEGY FOR CULTURAL SUSTAINABILITY AND ECONOMIC GROWTH

Tania Delgado

Associated Professor, Universidad El Bosque

✉ delgadotania@unbosque.edu.co, taniacatalina@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

The elements of the Cultural Heritage have brought new discussions and challenges because despite the recognition of their value they have been idolized and consequently confined in museum cases, disconnecting them from reality. This research has been developed from a Design framework and explores how the narrative character of the Oral Patrimony is able to connect these resources with their contemporary context and bearers; thus cultural goods become Storytellers (as any product), able to reveal their potential as resources of sustainable development at different levels (cultural, economic, environmental, political, etc).

Throughout some Design strategies (Emotional Design and Co-Design) people – cultural bearers can become active users and consumers of their territory and cultural property and have a meaningful approach (supported by Storytelling) that helps them to understand the potential of their Cultural Heritage in the construction of Creative Industries and therefore of a Creative Economy.

KEYWORDS: *Oral Patrimony, Cultural Patrimony, CoDesign, Emotional Design, Creative Industries.*

ORAL PATRIMONY: A RESOURCE THAT INTEGRATES COMMUNITIES WITH THEIR CULTURAL HERITAGE

The Oral Patrimony is structured by a rich platform of stories told from one generation to another where all the Cultural Heritage is present, because as the UNESCO has stated in The Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage (Paris, 2003): ‘Language is considered the vehicle of all the traditions and cultural expressions, even the language itself’.

Though it is completely intangible, it gathers all the wisdom and evolution about different social manifestations (such as carnivals, festive events, and daily life); artistic practices (like theatre and dances); the know-how concerning nature and the universe (agriculture, medicine, gastronomy, mythology, etc.); artisanal techniques (such as basketry, ceramics and textiles, among others); and their materialization typologies, as in the case of sites (historic places, archeological sites, and cultural landscape); as well as cultural objects (for example, books and handicrafts, among others).

The wisdom that these stories reveal is the result of a long process whereby every community consolidates around a cultural manifestation or practice, and through the oral ar-

chives of this cultural evolution wisdom can be perceived. For this reason any approach to the Oral Patrimony of a community clarifies the past of a territory, its people, and its culture.

In this way it is possible to establish the intrinsic narrative nature of the Oral Patrimony, which has all the potential for reinforcing the communication of the cultural goods with their cultural bearers. In fact, through the integration of oral resources and the visual features, present in the cultural goods, a stimulating narrative can be structured. Therefore, people can understand better the elements of their cultural heritage, and if the communicative interaction becomes a memorable experience a sense of belonging and consequently a reinforcement of the cultural identity can be furthered in the bearers.

STORYTELLING AND ORAL PATRIMONY: REMARKABLE CASES WHERE CULTURAL GOODS BECOME STORYTELLERS

The AESS Archivio di Etnografia e Storia Sociale della Regione Lombardia - Archive of Ethnography and Social Stories of the Lombardy Region, the London’s Voices exhibition-project, and the interactive spaces-exhibitions Sensible Map and

Sensitive City developed by Studio Azzurro are interesting examples that show how the Oral Patrimony of a place is a meaningful and rich complementary history to the one found in the traditional books.

An interesting example where the researchers have involved the inhabitants as Storytellers, making them feel like important characters of the construction and preservation of their Oral Patrimony, and therefore their Cultural Heritage, is the case of the AESS¹. This archive is an impressive work in which this public institution has been able to join different entities and people that have worked, gathering the Lombardy's Oral Patrimony for years.

Thanks to this effort there are more than 5,000 hours of records that contain documents of the Oral Patrimony of the Lombardy Region, which have been classified in different categories according to the topics (alimentation, art, religion, love, games, family matters, etc.); places (different towns and cities of Lombardy); protagonists (names of the Storytellers); typology (songs, stories, interviews, etc.); Intangible Patrimony (different festivities that have this recognition in this Italian region); and partner entities (names of the different entities and institutions that have collaborated in this collecting process).

These archives are available over the Internet and intend to publicize those unknown but meaningful aspects of the local communities of this Italian region, supporting the diffusion of the Lombardy's Cultural Heritage and fostering its reuse in the contemporary context. Through these stories many cultural manifestations (tangible and intangible) gain an emotional voice, since the narrations are full of memories that evidence the profound value of these goods for the people of this region.

In the case of the exhibition *London's Voices*² the process for collecting the stories was carried out by the Museum of London, throughout different projects of Oral History³ developed from the mid 1980s. Lewisham Voices (memories, stories and images of the people from the borough of Lewisham); Holidays of a lifetime (holiday experiences of the Londoners); London 16-19 (encouraging young people to tell their stories throughout songs and poems to make the Storytelling more appealing to them); and Women talk (exploring the challenging role of women during the 20th century), have been the four exhibitions that have preceded and become the basis of the London's Voices work.

Behind these exhibitions there is a significant example of a collaborative work with the communities, where throughout

group sessions, workshops, and individual interviews the Londoners, from different cultural backgrounds, got involved and engaged with the collection of the London Oral History. The main purpose of this work was to develop relations with the different communities that make up part of the multicultural context of this city.

On the other hand, for facilitating the participation of a large population, the group sessions managed common themes of the quotidian life that allowed all the participants to feel connected and able to share their experiences. After creating this first engagement, people were motivated to tell and to listen to stories in order to discover their favorite and most meaningful memories of each one. In this process the researchers could get to know different communities involved in the project, which helped to establish the methodologies and topics most adequate for each group.

Additionally, it was important to tell people how all these stories reflect their role in the continuous construction of London's Culture. In fact, all the oral archives were considered significant documents that reveal traditional practices and their transformation through time; and all the emotional facets that are always ingrained in these quotidian stories make them all the more special for the Storytellers and Story-listeners, deeply engaging both kinds of participants, and allowing this city to tell its story through the voices of its people.

In this way the boundaries of the Museum were breached in order to encourage a collaborative work between the Museum and the citizens, in which dialogue became the platform for sharing and negotiating the relevant elements of the Oral Patrimony, and therefore the cultural identity (Greenhill, 2007 and Simon, 2010)⁴ of this multicultural city.

Finally, in Sensible Map (inspired by a typical Moroccan city) and Sensitive City (inspired by some traditional Italian historic centers - Lucca, Siracusa, Matera, Chioggia, Spoleto and Trieste),⁵ the citizens gained the role of Storytellers or 'portatori di storie' (in English, 'bearers of stories', as Studio Azzurro call them) who describe their bonds with their cities in each story, helping simultaneously to reveal and reinforce the intangible weaves among inhabitants and the urban spaces. Somehow these exhibitions give a voice to every wall of these places, making the historic architecture not only a witness of countless happenings (many of them are cultural practices ingrained in the quotidian life of citizens), but also a storyteller.

In both cases there is a large projection of people walking, who can be stopped by the exhibition visitors with one touch. After this initial interaction the projected person stops and starts talking about their quotidian experiences in different spots of their historic cities. These 'portatori di storie' show throughout their narrations the emotional value that their cities have gained during the time, for being the scenarios

1 The AESS catalogue is available at: http://www.aess.regione.lombardia.it/ricerca/ricerca_src/home_page.php?sigla=aess_view

2 More information about this exhibition can be found in the document *London's Voices. Sharing oral history*, and on the website: <http://www.museumoflondon.org.uk/archive/london-voices/>

3 These projects of Oral History have become a meaningful process of collecting Londoners' stories.

4 These authors explain the importance of engaging the community in a collaborative work in order to better understand what identifies them.

5 Both cases can be found at: <http://www.studioazzurro.com/>

of a daily interaction that inevitably constructs personal ties between the citizens and their cities.

As a result each visit is an unrepeatable encounter between the visitors and the aspects that have built the identity of different places, bringing together people, continents, and heritage.

In this way Studio Azzurro's exhibitions stimulate a spontaneous performance in each visit, with the idea of creating an 'embodied experience' (Csordas, 1993, p.138) that engages visitors with their space and the material exhibited, which in these cases are distant communities, their culture, and territories.⁶

The analysis of these three cases reveals how the stories of the people can be perceived as the stories of a place and its cultural goods, because though a community lives the same history each member perceives it and experiences it in a particular way, thereby it is important to recognize the significance of the large amount of stories that reveal endless personal views and voices (Halbwachs, 1992, p.182).

Thus Storytelling and Oral Patrimony enable an understanding of the diverse connections among a territory (scenario); its people (protagonists); and its Cultural Heritage (inherited practices, manifestations, goods, etc.); or creative production, because "Storytelling allows visualization to reveal information as effectively and intuitively as if the viewer were watching a movie" (Gershon and Page, 2001, p.31).

THE FRAGILITY OF THE ORAL PATRIMONY

Since all these cultural resources have been archived in the memory of the bearers, which 'cannot retain and remember everything' (Lynch, 1972, p.36), this inherited and intangible knowledge is threatened and its risk of disappearance becomes imminent. For this reason, since the UNESCO Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage in 2003, different organizations worldwide have expressed their concern about these issues, recommending new approaches for the safeguarding of the Oral Patrimony, which guarantee a special support to the bearers-storytellers and the creation of new strategies that overcome the intangibility that makes Oral Patrimony even more vulnerable.

Thus the development of inventories is not the only priority because promoting the role of the bearers as active storytellers and transmitters of their knowledge (intangible heritage) is of crucial importance (Bouchenaki, 2004, p. 9) in avoiding situations where the death of a human encyclopedia means the disappearance of invaluable knowledge, like the Malian writer Amadou Hampaté Bâ said: 'In Africa, when an old person dies a library burns down'.

Therefore bearers might be encouraged to continue performing their practices as Storytellers (which is a way of struc-

⁶ In fact, Sensitive City was first displayed in the Italian pavilion of EXPO, Shanghai, in 2010, and later in Japan with the idea of confronting different cultures with the help of new technologies.

turing a strategy of social innovation) for getting naturally involved in the protection, preservation, and reinforcement of their own Cultural Heritage; strengthening simultaneously the memory of the storytellers and the community.

BUILDING CREATIVE INDUSTRIES FROM INHERITED CULTURAL KNOWLEDGE: A STRATEGY OF INTEGRAL SUSTAINABILITY AND SOCIAL INCLUSION

From another point of view, this Oral Patrimony reveals meaningful paths and develops knowledge for the construction of a sustainable future. These stories archive the experience and knowledge about a territory and its resources that should not be underestimated because, as the Indian Chef Manjit Gill affirms, 'We need to believe in the practices of the past and follow them. They are based on sustainability'.

In fact, the Oral Patrimony has an economic value that complements its cultural relevance. In the case of the AESS' archives most of the stories described several techniques of traditional agriculture forgotten, in spite of their incredible value for obtaining unique products such as artisanal alcoholic beverages (wine, lambrusco, grappa, etc.).

Interesting cases can be seen in many non-western communities, which are vivid examples of where cultural knowledge is the instrument for Sustainable Development (Serageldin, 1995, p. V). For instance, in the agricultural practices of Zimbabwe 'farmers are able to predict the onset of rain using such signs as changes in leaf color of some tree species, shifts in wind direction, cloud formation, temperature and relative humidity fluctuations, and bird and beetle songs and their seasonal migration. These signs are crucial in decision making relating to land preparation, planting and choice of plants' (Gata, 1995, p.12).

These agricultural practices have been shaped according to the conditions of the rural Zimbabwe, and reveal how its communities have a deep understanding of their environment and its resources, necessary for its sustainability. However many cultural assets that have been part of these ancestral sustainable visions are struggling with modernity, because there is a failure to respect cultural knowledge and its diversity from one place to another, throughout the imposition of modern technologies that underestimate the local inherited knowledge and practices (Gata, 1995, p.13).

For this reason there is a need for new approaches that not only encourage emotional encounters with the inherited culture (like in the exhibitions described before) but also show communities its value and its crucial role supporting development. Then new models should promote the continuity of the Cultural Patrimony at the core of the communities that bear it, without denying its functionality in the prosperity of a territory.

At the cultural level this perspective is also related with the concept of Creative Industries, which are based on the Cultural Patrimony (UNCTAD, 2008, p. 12) for structuring eco-

conomic paths from the resources ancestrally available in a territory; their main goal is to show communities the potential of this special property in their own development.

This strategy becomes a method of ‘Safeguarding without freezing’ or ‘Safeguarding and Valorization’, which means to preserve the essence of the cultural goods without denying its evolution or transformation; thereby new features can be articulated to the cultural goods in order to give them values that reinforce their capacity to endure and to become active resources in the reality of a territory and its people.

This idea inevitably involves changes in intangible and tangible cultural goods; an adjustment that makes them desirable products able to become part of current markets, without losing the essence that makes them unique, because that is the main asset for being competitive and highly differential in the market (Throsby, 2001).

From this perspective, different strategies of Design get a place in the Cultural Heritage ‘Safeguarding without freezing’ or ‘Safeguarding and Valorization’, and though this view proposes Re-Creation processes that alter the ancestral features of the Patrimony (for making them consume intangible and tangible products), the productive uses for the wellbeing of the communities validate these changes as part of a natural evolution, because cultural goods should become “always a work in progress, evolving, cumulative and structured” as Ms. Khalida Toumi, Minister of Culture of Algeria has said during the first session of the Intangible Heritage Committee in Algiers.

Shaping a Storytelling from the Oral Patrimony able to reveal new Paths of Development

The narrative proposed from the Oral Patrimony has a crucial role in this process because it gives a voice to cultural goods, not only for building a dialogue between bearers and these ancestral goods but also for revealing through this dialogue the knowledge and wealth behind the Cultural Heritage. Thus, different cultural goods can be revalued and reincorporated in the contemporary context, like in the case of innumerable food industries around the world, which have been structured from the inherited knowledge around traditional food, transmitted through Oral Tradition.

In this way it is possible to shape an incubator of knowledge based on the uncountable stories of the Oral Patrimony told by the bearers, recognizing them as human encyclopedias and establishing their inclusion in the construction of Creative Industries, which can intrinsically determine new ways of development more accurate in regards to the specific characteristics of each territory and community.

Building a Creative Economy with Industries based on Cultural Heritage and innovation

There is not a unique definition of Creative Economy, in fact this concept is still evolving but it is clear that it is ‘based on creative assets potentially generating economic growth and development’ (UNCTAD, 2008, p.4). Inside this concept is

also found the notion, Creative and Cultural Industries, which represent spaces for the production and re-creation of intangible and tangible goods that interconnect the creativity and culture with an economic projection.

Creative and Cultural Industries are characterized by having the input of human creativity in their production, which although is immersed in an economic context has a significance that goes beyond any economic value (UNCTAD, 2008, p. 10).

The interests of this project turn around the concept of Creative Industries, which are based on Cultural Heritage, giving economic values to traditional cultural expressions and products such as arts and crafts, festivals and celebrations, know-how, and cultural sites (like museums, archaeological sites, Historic Centers, cultural landscapes, etc.), among others (UNCTAD, 2008, p.12). However there are other traditional expressions (like the traditional medicine, gastronomy, agriculture, etc.) that have not been included in this category, but are part of the Cultural Heritage of any community, and it is important to recognize their potential in the construction of these special industries.

This use of Cultural Patrimony in the reinforcement of the economy intrinsically involves the human creativity, and their combination can ‘create extraordinary value and wealth’, as Howkins (2001, p.8) has affirmed, because this integration supports a parallel growth of the economy and the culture, empowering resources that have a unique hallmark given to them by the unrepeatable features of a Cultural Heritage.

In this way Creative Industries get recognized as ‘central in promoting and maintaining cultural diversity’. Since sustaining the Cultural Heritage (among other cultural resources of the modernity) in the contemporary context is a quest, which also intends to promote the respect of cultural diversity and social inclusion in the Sustainable Development and construction of a fairer economic model.

CODESIGN AND EMOTIONAL DESIGN IN THE CONSTRUCTION OF CREATIVE INDUSTRIES: NEW PATHS FOR THE SAFEGUARDING AND VALORIZATION OF CULTURAL HERITAGE

The affinity between the processes of Safeguarding and Valorization, and the Design practice, is not a coincidence, because the act of designing a product or a service is closely related to cultural values, such as aesthetics and human creativity, which are also ingrained aspects of the production of Cultural Patrimony.

This correlation (between culture and design) is the foundation of a platform that through different strategies of Design is able to promote a continuous evolution of Cultural Heritage (exploiting the creativity and inherited knowledge-wisdom), with the goal of producing contemporary cultural products (tangible or intangible) from the uniqueness and essence of the ancestral heritage.

In this process the Design creates a framework where the cultural property, that belongs to the patrimony of every community, is perceived as a set of intangible and tangible products that need to be recreated according to their contemporary bearers, who are also their main users and consumers. Through Design the renewed cultural goods take on an active role in the present of a place and its people, becoming lasting and beloved elements of the community that has inherited them, and most of the time does not have neither a close relation with them nor an idea of what to do with this patrimony.

Applying Design in these processes of Safeguarding and Valorization bridges the gap between Cultural Heritage (tangible and intangible) and the contemporary users-consumers-bearers, building an approach that gets strengthened throughout interaction (use and consumption), and consequently contributes to reinforce the sense of belonging and the cultural identity.

For these reasons it was determined both that the importance of building emotive relations with the renewed cultural goods and the recognition of the cultural bearers as main creators, possessors, and consumers-users of their Cultural Heritage, establishes the need for using strategies of Emotional Design (for building the mentioned emotive relations), and CoDesign (for recognizing the storytellers of the community as meaningful stakeholders) in the processes of reincorporating cultural goods within the reality of a territory. Thus it is possible to further the transformation of the cultural goods in the products required for the construction of successful Creative Industries.

Here the Storytelling acquires a significant role, and through Design it becomes an essential part of the renewed cultural products, giving them the capacity of socializing with the users-consumers in a way that goes further than functional aspects. In fact the Storytelling could give narrative tools to the cultural goods, and with them plenty of emotional values, taken from the Storytellers (community of bearers) that in every story create a weave that tangles their cultural property (tangible and intangible) with personal insights and feelings, showing the significance of the social inclusion in this process.

CoDesign in the Construction of Creative Industries: Storytellers of Cultural Patrimony in the Process of Cultural Entrepreneurship

There is a growing recognition of the power of stories for sparking imagination, conveying values, and inspiring collaborative action
(Doty, 2003, p. 3).

Inside every community Storytelling is an essential part of daily life. Thanks to this multifaceted tool of communication, entertainment, and knowledge transmission, among other things, the world has been able to know its history and the uncountable aspects that have been involved in its transformation throughout different periods. Traditional storytellers

describe the cultural knowledge and practices of a community (the know-how about construction, handcrafting, agriculture, natural medicine, traditional gastronomy, etc.) giving essential information about the environmental features, potential, limitations, and evolution through time.

Storytelling provides the basis for the use of this ancestral knowledge in the development of strategies that promote the economy and wellbeing in each territory. Furthermore, when the local communities realize that they are the ones that truly understand their environments, their self-esteem gets nourished, encouraging their participation as protagonists of the processes behind development. In this way culture connects with the environment, economy, and society in order to project unique strategies of Sustainable Development that respond to the characteristics of each context.

Recognizing local communities as the main creators and bearers of ancestral knowledge, reveals the importance of giving them a prominent role in the transformation or recreation of these resources for the construction of Creative Industries, because in this way they will be kept close to their cultural property, relating to it not only as part of their past, but also as evolving resources deeply connected to their cultural identity through their transformations. The construction of this connection makes possible to promote processes with the permanent consent of the community for validating the transformation of the cultural resources, as it was underlined in the first session of the Intangible Heritage Committee in Algiers: 'Some noted their own national experiences where safeguarding efforts developed with communities succeeded, while those developed without community involvement or consent failed. Finally, some Members suggested that the criteria should focus on the substantive involvement of communities rather than the formalities of demonstrating their consent; if they were truly involved at all stages that was the best evidence of their consent' (The Intangible Heritage Messenger, 2007, p.3).

In this way bearers participate not only as Storytellers able to reveal the richness archived in their memories, but also as co-designers who, just like any other stakeholder of the design process (users, consumers, producers, sellers, etc.) provide valuable information that can help to develop new cultural goods (tangible or intangible), that can be projected with a successful reception in global markets.

Thus the construction of Creative Industries from the Oral Patrimony becomes a participatory space for re-contextualizing cultural goods, and this attitude is also synchronized with the recognition made in 2012 by UNESCO in the 40th anniversary of the World Heritage Convention, where the central topic was 'World Heritage and Sustainable Development: the Role of Local Communities'.⁷

7 More information available at: <http://whc.unesco.org/en/40years/>.

Emotional Design in the Construction of Creative Industries: Recreating Cultural Goods for the Integral Development of Territories and their People

There are things that we regard as important to preserve for future generations. They may be significant due to their present or possible economic value, but also because they create a certain emotion within us, or because they make us feel as though we belong to something – a country, a tradition, a way of life.

(from: UNESCO, What is Intangible Cultural Heritage?).

As it was described in the previous paragraphs, the relation between Cultural Patrimony and their contemporary communities involves emotive feelings, which in the end validate the relevance or irrelevance of some cultural goods and therefore their perdurability at the core of a community. Throughout the vision of Emotional Design, diverse types of cultural goods could be enhance, for arising emotions that could make their bearers (also their main consumers and users) re-value, retake, and reincorporate their intangible and tangible Cultural Patrimony in their present.

The emotive relationship described above is a fertile terrain for applying strategies of Emotional Design focus to reinforce the bonding between bearers and their cultural goods, not just for ensuring a consumption, but for guaranteeing the reincorporation of cultural heritage resources in the lifestyles of contemporary bearers-users-consumers.

Additionally, throughout Storytelling the cultural goods acquire the emotions of the stories, reinforcing their value and significance; somehow the products designed with a narrative that integrates visual-aesthetic aspects and the Storytelling present in the Oral Patrimony, capture in their design their own history (that clarifies how and why these goods were created, used, and transformed during the time), strengthening the invisible web among the past and the present of the Cultural Heritage.

Aromáticas del Alisal⁸ - Tisanes of the Alisal is an interesting case developed in a small Colombian town called Guacamayas by the NGO Fundación Espiral de Servicio⁹ - Spiral of Service Foundation. This project demonstrates how Storytelling elderly transmit their knowledge about plants to the new generations, for the creation of an industry of tisanes that has achieved a significant autonomy showing the local community the potential of its own cultural knowledge.

The participation of the elderly, adults, youngsters, and children was a key point in making this project, because the elderly and adults became the guides for several explorations in this rural territory, helping children and youngsters

to identify the different species thanks to their experience and knowledge. During these explorations the wise guides told uncountable stories, recounting the secret ingredients that their mothers and families used for cooking and curing. In this way each journey was an experience that, throughout Storytelling, showed the values of the natural resources and cultural practices present in this territory.

After this initial stage was promoted in the Alisal's school the creation of several organic orchards of medicinal, aromatic, and culinary plants, managed by the children and youngsters, and under the supervision of the elderly and adults, kept alive a chain by which mature and new generations got connected in the transmission of cultural knowledge.

Eventually these processes led into the commercialization of these products,¹⁰ in two presentations fresh-green and dehydrated, creating Aromáticas del Alisal, which is a clear example of a Creative Industry that encourages the transmission of the knowledge about plants to the youngest guys of the community, through encounters among elderly and adults with children and youngsters.¹¹ Additionally, the presentation of these products has been designed according to their proposed role as Storyteller (transmitter of cultural knowledge not only at the interior of the Alisal's community but also towards the consumers) able to capture the attention of contemporary markets.

Another meaningful case has been developed by the FAI – Fondo Ambiente Italiano – Italian Environment Fund in the project FAI che giochiamo?¹² — FAI let's play? —, which provides an emotive service for exploring different historical sites in the Italian territory. This intangible product takes advantage of the feelings that these sites awake in young generations, related to magical and fantastic images that if well managed, could positively influence the sense of belonging these special consumers-users-bearers have towards these historic places.

In this project the FAI organizes tours inside different Italian cultural sites for students of any age, with the purpose of offering an educative experience with plenty of perceptive stimuli that encourages an enjoyable learning process. With costumes of the mythical personages that have been part of these scenarios' history and mythology, there is an embodied experience that exploits the theatrical potential and the imagination of the participants and makes them feel part of those tales.

From these cases it is possible to see how Safeguarding and Valorization processes have developed new products (tangi-

8 The Alisal is an area that belongs to the town of Guacamayas, which is remotely located in the Colombian Andes. The isolation of this region is closely related to its problems of poverty, violence and illiteracy, among others.

9 Additional information in <http://fundacionlaespiral.kk5.org/> and Facebook: Aromáticas del Alisal and Fundacion Laespiral.

10 For the commercialization of these products an image has already been designed (package and logotype). The products have already been timidly commercialized, but there is still a lack of strategies to bring these tisanes to consolidated markets.

11 This knowledge is an Intangible Cultural Heritage formally recognized by the UNESCO.

12 More information about FAI che giochiamo? and the Fondo Ambiente Italiano can be found at: <http://www.fondoambiente.it>.

ble and intangible) that understand contemporary consumers-users, who nowadays search for products that go further than functional needs, and satisfy their most emotional and spiritual expectations (Schmitt 1999, p.22); (Demirbilek and Sener 2003, p.1348), which in this case are inevitably related to the cultural identity and the sense of belonging that stir the uniqueness attached to any cultural good of the Patrimony.

CONCLUSION

From this analysis it was possible to conclude the innovative aspects of this proposal, which are:

- The recognition of Design, a discipline usually neglected in these matters, providing new possibilities to confront the different challenges (Safeguarding and Valorization among others), which are threatening the worldwide Cultural Heritage.
- This proposal also gives a significant recognition to the possibilities that the Oral Patrimony can offer in the development of a territory and its communities, since the wisdom present in each story, reveals the potential of different cultural resources.
- The weaving of a cultural-economic system, through Storytelling, is another innovative aspect that recognizes the economic value of each story.
- The recognition of Design not only as a Cultural Industry but also as a tool able to support the Re-Creation of the cultural property for the construction of Creative Industries. This aspect also contributes to the changing of an economic model, towards the Creative Economy.

In this way, through Design the cultural resources will have more opportunities for being active participants of the present and future of the communities, not only at emotional levels, related to the memories of a romantic and idealized past, but also at sustainable levels that give Cultural Heritage a new possibility of being the promoter of Sustainable Development. As Hawkes (2001, p.12) says, 'a sustainable society depends upon a sustainable culture'.

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DISRUPTING HEALTH AND SOCIAL CARE BY DESIGN

Paul A. Rodgers, Andy Tennant

Northumbria University, School of Design, Newcastle upon Tyne NE1 8ST, UK

✉ paul.rodgers@northumbria.ac.uk, andy.tennant@northumbria.ac.uk

Katie Dodd

Carers Centre Newcastle, Newcastle upon Tyne, NE6 1DN, UK

✉ katie@carerscentrenewcastle.org.uk

ABSTRACT

In the UK, over six million people are unpaid informal carers for an ill, frail family member, or a friend who can't manage to live independently, or whose health or wellbeing would deteriorate without their help. This saves the UK taxpayer over £119 billion a year (Carers UK, 2011). Although the role and experience of informal carers is unique to their situation, it is known that their health suffers and that they have an increased rate of mental and physical health problems. This paper describes an on-going collaborative project between the first two authors and a carer organisation in Newcastle upon Tyne, England. The work presented here illustrates unique and innovative disruptive design interventions that re-imagine social and health care through participative design events. The paper will present some of the current findings from this on-going research and indicate how disruptive design innovation can support the development and delivery of radical future health and social care provision.

KEYWORDS: *Disruption, Design, Care, Interventions.*

BACKGROUND

There are an estimated 6.4 million people in the UK providing unpaid care and support to ill, frail and disabled friends and family members. Families provide the majority of care in the UK, outstripping social care services and private care providers combined. This contribution is worth an estimated £119 billion a year to the UK economy — more than the total cost of the National Health Service (NHS) in the UK. However, caring usually comes at great cost to carers. Many are forced to give up work to care, at the same time as they are faced with the considerable additional costs of disability. This means that, alongside the personal costs of ill-health, for many families, disability and caring pushes them into debt and hardship.

In England alone, around three million households contain an unpaid informal carer, which represents huge social care and NHS cost savings. The official figures from the 2011 Census show that there are over 25,000 adult carers living in Newcastle upon Tyne, which is almost 10% of the city's population. Although the role and experience of informal carers is unique to their situation, and caring can be a rich source of satisfaction, it is also known that their health suffers and that they have an increased rate of mental and physical health problems. Thus, it is very important that we identify informal carers so that we can provide much needed help and support. This paper will go on to describe support in the form of a series of unique and innovative disruptive design workshops that are helping Carers Centre Newcastle (CCN) re-imagine

their social and health care service through participative design events. The first two authors and care support workers at CCN believe the disruptive design approach, and the insights that have been revealed as a result have the potential to achieve more than the act of simply ploughing more money into social and health care could achieve.

WHO CARES?

In the UK, a carer is anyone of any age who provides unpaid support to family or friends who could not manage without this help. This could be caring for a relative, partner or friend who is ill, frail, disabled, or has mental health or substance misuse problems. Anyone can become a carer; carers come from all walks of life, all cultures, and can be of any age. Many feel they are doing what anyone else would do in the same situation of looking after their mother, son, brother, or best friend, and just getting on with it. Carers experience many difficulties in their caring situations. For example, a carer could be someone looking after a new baby with a disability or caring for an elderly family member. In the UK, informal carers are the largest source of care and support. However, caring for a family member or friend is very demanding and can lead to a number of other related problems including:

- Carers facing a life of poverty, isolation, frustration, ill health and depression.

- Carers giving up a regular financial income, future employment prospects, and pension rights.
- Carers juggling several jobs with their caring responsibilities.
- Carers struggling alone not knowing that help is available to them.
- Carers' lack of access to information and financial support that is vital in managing the impact of caring on their own lives.
- Carers with multiple caring roles — often referred to as 'sandwich carers', who are frequently older women who care for relatives (e.g. a mother with dementia and a daughter who misuses drugs).

CARERS CENTRE NEWCASTLE (CCN)

Carers Centre Newcastle (CCN) opened in April 2004 in direct response to carers who had campaigned for seven years to have a place of their own in Newcastle City Centre. The campaigners wanted a setting that had no stigma attached to it, unlike a clinic or hospital. CCN originally operated as part of Newcastle Healthy City, but since 2004 has now become an independent charity and company limited by guarantee. CCN's vision is to improve the quality of carers' lives in and around the city of Newcastle upon Tyne and to work towards a future where Newcastle carers are recognised and valued, they are able to overcome inequality, receive support, information and advice, and are able to exercise choice and control through their caring journey and beyond, so that carers can balance their caring role and maintain their desired quality of life.

CCN offer award winning caring services that are confidential, non-judgemental, and impartial. They provide information, one-to-one carer support, training, and opportunities for carers to join groups or take part in events and activities as well as access sessions with CCN's complementary therapists and counsellors. The caring service process at CCN begins when a service user contacts CCN. At this point, one of CCN's Carer Support Workers will carry out a confidential assessment based upon the individual circumstances of the carer and the person they care for. At this stage, CCN may refer the carer to appropriate organisations for specialist services. Moreover, CCN provide carers with support in the format they are most comfortable with, which could be over the telephone, a home visit, a Centre visit, or by email.

However, against the backdrop of the failures of global financial capitalism (Bazzichelli & Cox, 2013), the widespread austerity measures and the quite sudden and dramatic general economic changes to the world in 2008, this has had a serious and significant impact on caring, carers, their families, and the work that CCN undertakes. Moreover, as changes occur to the population of Newcastle upon Tyne in terms of age, illness, disability, and diversity the number of carers will increase, as they will generally across the UK. The current austerity measures and diminishing budgets within health and

social care will reduce the number of people who are eligible to receive support and the move to deliver 'care closer to home' will increase the responsibility and reliance on carers. This is further exacerbated by the UK's on-going welfare reforms, changes in housing policies, employment and training opportunities, and other issues that all add up to a 'perfect storm' for carers.

THE DESIGN DISRUPTION GROUP

The Design Disruption Group is a small group of design researchers, educators, and practitioners whose collective objective is to bring about positive change via disruptive design acts. The group has been working together for over three years and has disruptively intervened in a number of contemporary situations in the private, public sector, and third sector. Example design interventions include projects such as 'sticker' campaigns on the streets of Edinburgh, 'fortune cookie' services for a Chinese restaurant in Gateshead, 'celebratory brass plaques' on the walls and alleyways of Newcastle, 'street lamppost data prompts' in conjunction with the Multiple Sclerosis (MS) society, a 'one week entrepreneur' project with the YMCA, and several others (see, <http://designdisruptiongroup.wordpress.com/> for more examples).

The on-going collaboration between Carers Centre Newcastle and the Design Disruption Group was established against the backdrop of some of the most challenging socioeconomic times that we have faced. Part of the rationale for this collaboration is that it will enable CCN to build a strong evidence base and depart from a reliance on anecdotal information or hearsay about what the real health and social care issues are. This evidence is paramount when making the case for carers to local and national decision makers. Health and social care providers repeatedly talk about the need to invest in 'prevention and early intervention' but struggle to move the budgets away from acute and critical services. Regional and national health and social care policy makers need to see real evidence of need, what can make a difference, and how it can or will work. Thus, the on-going collaboration seeks to contribute to discussions in Newcastle and elsewhere, to assist commissioners, local and national policy makers, and service managers to understand the benefits of investing in carers.

Initially, the Design Disruption Group held a series of workshops with CCN's staff members, including their Training and Development Manager, Carer Support and Development Workers, Information and Communications Co-ordinator, and Volunteer Counsellors. During these initial workshop sessions, CCN staff outlined what they wished to achieve from the collaboration. The key aim of the ongoing collaborative project is to help CCN continue to deliver an excellent service in the face of a number of exceptional circumstances including the widespread austerity measures, the increasing elderly population, and the increasing diversity and number of carers living in and around Newcastle upon Tyne, and diminishing budgets within health and social care. CCN's work is further exacerbated by the UK's on-going welfare reforms,

changes in housing policies, employment and training opportunities, and other issues that all add up to a ‘perfect storm’ for carers. The main aim for the first two authors (as two of the founding members of the Design Disruption Group) is to engage with real world issues and use design as a tool to enact real positive change. The Design Disruption Group in this project wish to utilise disruptive design interventions to ensure that all carers will receive greater choice and control in their lives as well as exploring the more general role that disruptive design interventions might play in improving the physical, mental health and wellbeing of carers, care support workers, and other stakeholders.

DISRUPTIVE DESIGN WORKSHOPS

The main aim of the disruptive design workshops is to break the cycle of well-formed opinions, strategies, mindsets, and ways-of-doing, that tend to remain unchallenged in the health and social care of vulnerable individuals in the UK. Disruptive Design is an approach that the first two authors have developed over several years (Rodgers et al., 2011; Rodgers & Tennant, 2012; Rodgers et al., 2013). A disruptive design approach encourages the development of richer, more varied solutions to everyday issues by emphasising fun (Bisson & Luckner, 1996), ‘safe failure’, and doing things in ways that one wouldn’t normally do. In a disruptive design workshop, the emphasis is placed on having fun, relaxing, and trying things out in a stress-free environment where participants are encouraged to fail fast and fail often without fear.

In essence, the disruptive design workshops exploit techniques and approaches developed by the authors that provide opportunities for participants to experiment in a relaxed, stress-free environment with expert facilitators. Most of the research in public social and health care seeks to evaluate intervention effectiveness and value for money. In contrast, however, this work proposes to develop a series of disruptive design interventions and assess how they might improve carers’ lives in the North East of England. Given the extremely challenging nature of the informal caring situation in the UK, the main aims of the collaborative research are to:

- Help change society’s perceptions of caring in the UK through a series of disruptive design workshops and interventions (i.e. products, systems, services).
- Create a series of designed interventions that will help carers access support before they hit ‘crisis point’ when their health is sometimes irreparably damaged.
- Help identify the major day-to-day consequences of caring for people through the use of disruptive design techniques and approaches.
- Consider how prevention and early intervention (e.g. designed products, systems, services) could enable carers to have greater choice and control.
- ‘Formally invite’ carers to participate/collaborate in the creation of the designed interventions.

It is envisaged that this work will contribute to scholarly debates on how social design, innovation in general, and disruptive design innovation in particular can support the design, development, and delivery of health and social care services. This exceptional and important partnership between the first two authors and a third sector organization, established to represent the needs of carers in the North East of England, and to raise their concerns and issues nationally, offers a number of valuable opportunities for wider public engagement with the health and social care sector in the UK.

SOCIAL CARE BY DESIGN METHODOLOGY

This on-going work adopts an iterative, research-through-design mixed-methods approach where the first two authors and collaborating partner (CCN) are involved in the generation, collection, evaluation, and interpretation of both quantitative and qualitative forms of information. This approach has advantages over other research approaches particularly relating to the development of reliable explanations (Cresswell, 2003). Thus far, the work has utilized a number of research approaches and tools including participatory design workshops, carer surveys and care support worker interviews, and design probes (Gaver et al., 2004) during the collaborative activities with CCN. The participatory design (sometimes known as co-design) nature of this research has endeavoured to actively involve all stakeholders (e.g. carers, care support workers, policy makers, health and social care experts, citizens) in the design process of creating designed products, systems, and services that are intended to meet end users’ and other stakeholders’ needs and be ultimately usable. As such, this ongoing collaborative work seeks to address the following research questions:

- How can disruptive design interventions help ensure that all carers will receive greater choice and control in their lives?
- What role can disruptive design interventions (i.e. designed products, systems, services) play in improving the physical, mental health, and wellbeing of carers?
- Can disruptive design interventions support informal carers to have a life of their own outside of their caring role, including a social life, in work and education and training?
- Can disruptive design interventions contribute to ensure that carers do not suffer financially as a result of their caring role?
- Can disruptive design interventions ensure that carers are treated as expert partners in care?

The participatory design approach adopted in this project supports innovative ways of creating design interventions that are more responsive and appropriate to the end users’ cultural, emotional, spiritual, and practical needs. This approach is focused on collaborative processes and procedures of design that promotes user empowerment and democratization. In the research described in this paper, participants

(i.e. carers, service users, Carers Centre Newcastle care workers, and other relevant stakeholders) have been invited to collaborate with the first two authors during a series of innovative disruptive design sessions. The innovative disruptive design sessions have allowed the carers, service users, Carers Centre Newcastle employees, the first two authors, and other relevant stakeholders to collaborate during several stages of the innovative process. That is, everyone has participated during the initial explorations and defining the issues to be addressed, to help identify the key issues, and to focus potential ideas for interventions, during intervention development, and in helping evaluate any proposed design interventions. As such, the methodology proposed here is both highly innovative in the context of health and social care, and truly collaborative in nature.

A NEW MODEL OF CARE

Given the severe socioeconomic circumstances that CCN are being asked to work within, the first two authors set out to understand more about CCN's work and the key activities involved in providing health and social care. CCN are faced with an on-going crisis in that their award winning carer services are hugely over-subscribed and demand far outstrips supply. Their carer services are regularly assessed as 100% in terms of the service user satisfaction rates and this only adds to the clamber for their unique service. As each month passes, the number of enquiries that CCN receives increases significantly. Moreover, diminishing budgets within health and social care have reduced the number of people who are eligible to receive support and the move to deliver 'care closer to home' has increased the responsibility and reliance on carers. Coupled with national welfare reforms, changes in housing policies, employment and training opportunities, and other pressures all adds up to a 'perfect storm' for carers and carer service professionals in the UK.

As part of one of our initial disruptive design sessions with CCN, we asked their care support workers to 'Draw What CCN Does'. We suggested that this might involve them drawing a diagram or constructing a collage of images. We also suggested that the illustrations might be abstract or highly descriptive and that they should minimise the use of text in their illustrations and only use text if absolutely necessary. We also advised them that the images might focus on all of CCN's work or just on one aspect of CCN's day-to-day work. We provided the CCN staff with a series of pre-determined rubber stamps and ink and the majority of the participants utilized these in their drawing of 'What CCN Does'. A recurring theme in the participants' images was the concept of CCN as a 'transformational agent'. That is, the participants viewed CCN's role in the overall care service as one where the carers would receive support from CCN, be transformed via one or more of these services (e.g. 'trips out', 'relaxation', 'pampering', etc.), and then 'fly away' to get on with the rest of their lives.

CCN'S 'A TO Z CHARTER OF CARE'

As is commonly known, a manifesto is a public declaration of an organisation's policy and aims. In a political context, for example, a political party or political candidate typically presents their manifesto before an election. The origin of the word manifesto comes from the Italian 'manifestare', meaning 'make public', and 'manifestus', meaning 'obvious'. Similarly, a charter is a written grant by a country's legislative or sovereign power, by which an institution such as a company, university, or city is created and its rights and privileges defined. A charter, for example, can be a written constitution or description of an organization's functions. In a design context, manifestos and charters are fairly common phenomena (Danchev, 2011). A well-known example is *The Munich Design Charter*, published in *Design Issues* in 1991, signed by Dieter Rams and many of the other leading designers of the era. In that seminal paper, Rams et al. are well aware of design's responsibilities in all parts of contemporary life and as such *The Munich Design Charter* proclaimed that design must concern itself with '...economy as well as ecology, with traffic and communication, with products and services, with technology and innovation, with culture and civilization, with sociological, psychological, medical, physical, environmental, and political issues, and with all forms of social organization' (Rams et al., 1991).

Given the crisis in the carer service that CCN currently finds itself in, Rodgers and Tennant, as part of their disruptive design work, asked the CCN staff to write their own 'A to Z Charter of Care'. The intention of this activity was to help the CCN staff think more deeply about the service that they provide and also to help them 'professionalise' their service more. Like Rams et al.'s *Munich Design Charter* earlier, the tone of the CCN 'A to Z Charter of Care' is serious in its delivery and is intended to support the CCN staff articulate better their care service for the future years to come. Figure 1 shows the A to Z responses as created by the CCN team. The intention is to design and develop these letters further into finished pieces and hang them on the walls of CCN's new offices in Newcastle upon Tyne. As can be seen, CCN's 'A to Z Charter of Care' as

Figure 4. CCN's 'A to Z Charter of Care'

articulated by the care support workers themselves is: Aware – Befriend – Care/Control – Developing – Equality – Fresh – Give/Genuine – Helpful – Inspiring/Ideas – Judgement – Kick [problem] – Life – Mellow – Non-judgemental – Observe – Practical – Questioning – Radical – Structure – Time – Unusual – Very focused – Wonderful – eXciting – Yours – Zoned in. This simple disruptive exercise has actually revealed some significant aspects of CCN's work. In the A to Z above, there are some obvious responses such as 'care' and 'helpful', but there are others that have a much deeper meaning and resonate more with the crisis situation that CCN currently experiences, such as 'structure' (the need for more) and 'time' (the lack of).

CONCLUSIONS / OUTCOMES

This ongoing collaborative project between the first two authors and the CCN staff has delivered a number of positive outcomes thus far. First, the project has helped contribute to scholarly work on how disruptive design innovation can support the development and delivery of health and social care interventions in practice. That is, this work will lead to the production of a number of scholarly papers and articles for appropriate outlets that will increase the visibility of how design, as an instrument of change, can play a pivotal role in health and social care contexts, which will encourage further research. This article is just one of several planned for this ongoing research.

Second, the partnership between the first two authors and CCN has resulted in an application being made to the Arts and Humanities Research Council (UK) for a new collaborative doctoral student. The proposed PhD researcher will work closely with the CCN team members who have a strong reputation for their care provision and a proven track record in excess of fifteen years, and provide an opportunity to develop the primary research skills that are essential in a future doctoral graduate. CCN have numerous links with local, regional, and national bodies, and participate in many multi-agency initiatives that impact on carers and/or the people they care for such as Newcastle Council, Newcastle Acute Hospitals Trust, PROPS North East, and Barnardo's Young Carers. The opportunity for the PhD researcher to immerse him or herself in this research and practitioner network will be invaluable. The development of participatory design skills, the support of CCN's local, regional and national network, and an emphasis on developing disruptive design interventions for real world issues will build the skills necessary for the PhD researcher to undertake a successful academic or commercial career in the future.

Third, the project has helped establish an important partnership between Northumbria University and a third sector organization that will help represent the needs of carers in the North East of England and raise their concerns and issues nationally. The ongoing collaboration has also offered a valuable opportunity for a widening public engagement with the health and social care sector in the North East of Eng-

land. In so doing, the research has supported the missions of Northumbria University and CCN, and aligns with targeted priorities for public engagement identified by the Arts and Humanities Research Council (UK).

Finally, the ongoing collaboration will work towards a number of specific outcomes for both academic and public audiences in the form of scholarly papers, popular articles, web material, and community engagement sessions. The project will also strengthen the links between Northumbria University, CCN, and the larger regional knowledge community, which will help build a strong platform for future collaboration, research, and dissemination in the important area of how disruptive design interventions can support the development and delivery of health and social care in practice.

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DESIGN EMOTION BRAND IMAGES ENHANCE SOCIAL VALUE, INSPIRE CHANGE AND INTENSIFY SOCIAL TRANSFORMATION

Stephen T.F. Poon
Taylor's University
✉ stephentfpoon@aol.com

ABSTRACT

Brand images spanning a myriad of business applications in advertising, branding and marketing activities have surpassed functional, commercial and financial considerations. Brand image-makers and marketers foray into broader discussions to demonstrate brands' inherent value and position as an emotional element of personal consumption and social interactions. This study seeks to understand the connection between the multitudes of conjured and perceived brand images and their unique capabilities to engage with specific consumers. Gathering survey data from the Malaysian urban consumer segment, this study aims to gain insight into emerging marketing literature, which attests to the emotional and social roles of brand image. Results reveal consumers' increased awareness and perception of today's successfully marketed brands, and a positive image emerges when brands visibly demonstrate target consumer engagement with emotional benefits, ideas that inspire social change and intensify social transformation. Social experiences with brands are a leading factor in enhancing marketing management strategies today, as businesses have greater opportunities to address, contribute to, and facilitate relevant social conversations through salient brand images.

KEYWORDS: *Brand Image, Brand Identity, Emotional Benefits, Social Value, Consumer Experience*

INTRODUCTION

Brand Image vs. Brand Identity: Some Term Definitions

Brands as a marketing concept and a social phenomenon have always been hard to characterise or describe utilising key definitions, making its study both a stimulating and reflective discourse in the development of marketing management perspectives. Dr Philip Kotler, distinguished marketing professor, sets the stage for this discussion by defining brand image as 'a set of beliefs that consumers hold about a particular brand' (2005, p. 282). Products manufactured, sold, and distributed by a particular company under a particular name as such carry a distinct image, and consumers would ascribe, interpret, or construct their own set of cognitive or affective responses that bears meaning to themselves or others, based on experiences, emotional benefits, social symbolisms and other dimensions (Aaker, 1991, 1992, 1996; Keller, 1993).

The American Marketing Association (2008) defines 'brand' more perfunctorily, as 'a name, term, sign, symbol, design, or a combination of features that identifies the goods or services of one seller or group of sellers and differentiates them from those of other sellers'. A brand projects the image of a particular organisation, product or service that consumers associate with, and marketing the brand image means making a careful selection of marketing mix criteria, considering the economic, cultural and social conditions which influence consumers' buying behaviours (Lake, 2009).

Global brand strategy consultant Professor David Aaker define brand identity as 'a unique set of brand associations that the brand strategist aspires to create or maintain' (Aaker, 1996, p.68). By extension, brands, whether they are the outcome of consumers' impressions and perceptions, but in having intrinsic equity value as economic entities, must be managed systematically (Keller, 1993). Omnipresent brands find their way to retailers and consumers in every aspect as a result of

functional and symbolic image congruity or alignment in people's impression, awareness, product involvement or utility, lifestyles, needs, and aspirations (Jing Hu et al, 2012). Every interaction with a brand counts, and advertising can undeniably affect society's perception of brand images; from memorable designs, logos, and slogans that compete for attention; billboards, magazines, websites, and a host of tangibles and intangibles (Jing Hu et al., 2012, p.2).

Branding processes and activities go along with marketing ideas to consumers to increase recognition and differentiation from competitors (McEnally & de Chernatony, 1999, p.17), yet volatile markets increase brands' susceptibility to competitive marketing in global environments, unless companies have long term positioning strategies mapped out (Ries & Trout, 1981, cited in McEnally & de Chernatony, 1999, p.13). It thus behoves that success in brand-building campaigns and brand loyalty relationships go hand-in-hand with understanding consumers (Light, 1994). Malik et al. (2012) argue for businesses to invest time to survey, research, define, and reinforce the brand in creating positive consumer awareness, top-of-mind recall and salience, leading to preference, purchase intention, and loyalty. Other studies view the relative construct of brand images: Kim et al. (2008), for instance, describe unique service as that which carries a brand image in consumers' minds, and that is identified and positioned to stand out from competitors.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

Brands have evolved from their traditional missions in pursuit of profit and the promotion of consumerism, to providing a range of personalised promises and added value to engender loyalty. The aim of this research is to examine links between consumer attitudes and perceptions of brand images' emotional design construct and the impact that results from their evolving roles in inspiring change and intensifying social transformation.

Driven by development in brand research, the current study attempts to answer several key questions, namely:

- What underlying relationships are conveyed by brand images today?
- How do consumer interaction and experiences with these images correlate to their emotional and social needs fulfilment?
- How could brand images communicate emotional benefits, which reflect consumers' social values and aspirations for change?

The objectives of this study are to review the role of brands through their economic and social contexts in order to understand brands' contributions in terms of psychological and emotional benefits, and social value. This study attempts to analyse the level of brand image awareness among a sampling of survey respondents from the urban demographical segment in Malaysia, and to determine the connection of brand image to purchasing behaviour.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The researcher begins studying a selection of literature, to develop perspectives to the question often raised, 'Why the buzz about brands?'. This is premised on the general public assumption that brands are mere corporate identity emblems and logos. Misconceptions and distorted ideas about brands may impact judgment and produce negative sentiments towards organisations (Pallotta, 2011). Brands in fact communicate more than marketplace information through ubiquitous logos. Kotler and Keller (2009) argue that brands affect businesses besides being associated with products: in the acceleration globalised environment, their roles and agents of customer loyalty permeate markets in different economic, cultural, and social conditions. The benefit of strong brand images not only sustains market equity for the business in the long run, but shapes economic opportunities through their indirect role in maintaining economic and social progress in terms of enhanced living standards, educational and job opportunities, health, safety, transportation, and much more. This paper argues for a broader impact of the influence of brand images through four key roles: namely, that it rationalises consumer interaction; facilitates economic development, creates social value; promotes innovation and cooperation and removes cross-cultural barriers, thus inspiring social transformation. The following sections further this discussion with case study examples of the roles of brand image constructs.

Brand Image in Consumer Interaction

Social entrepreneur and *Harvard Business Review* blogger Dan Pallotta (2011) believes that a brand 'is peoples' gut feeling about the organisation', and that in and within every level of customer interaction lays the signifier of their concern or interest in that brand, this view accords with the thought-provoking commentaries on brand positioning strategies undertaken by Ries and Trout in the 1980s (Malik et al., 2012, p.13070).

Brand identities rationalise consumer rights advocacy efforts via tangible brand promises (Trout, 2008), that consumers may expect to enjoy assurance of quality, integrity, and reliability in the provision of goods or services, such as displaying precise information, exceptional customer service and warranties, compliance with environmental, health, safety and labour regulations and other consumer protection benchmarks (Hilton, 2003). Aside from selling benefits, respectable brands in the marketplace assure consumers of quality, and the use of brand design elements help companies meet its consumers confidently. Brand images reflect enjoyment of particular aspects of consumption and social status, besides communicating an individual's aspirational values and enriching consumers' shared connections (Saade, 2010). Consumer behaviour and marketing research study the relationships between brand personalities, self-identity, and social interests, and how these concepts influence and correlate with target audience's expectations, self-expression and experiences (Aaker, 1996; Malik et al, 2012; McEnally & de Chernatony, 1999, p.16). Self-confidence, status, and aspiration are talking points via

associative brands, designed to affect one's image and express inner attributes. Brands, which represent preferences in food, clothing, arts, music, and hobbies, enhance followers' ability to acquaint themselves with like-minded people. Vitality, for businesses to develop, manage, and project the brand personality that fits target audiences, brand image advertising must have relevance, salience and significance to the latter's characteristics, backgrounds, and inclinations. With globalisation of markets driving economic growth, strategic brand awareness must take into account multicultural contexts in order to be realised (Palumbo and Herbig, 2000). Additionally, the pervasiveness of brands across cultural milieus is a result of being communicated with greater freedom in traditional, international and niche media (Kotler et al., 2005, p.773). The ease by which brands engage consumers makes them effective as a cultural tool: as such, marketers must improve awareness and insights on their related appeals, as the dialogue between what brands represent and the way this influences consumers becomes a close integration of knowledge and practice (Kotler & Keller, 2009).

Brand Image in Economic Development

Miriam Greenberg in her book *Branding New York* reflects on how the 'image crisis', which struck New York City in the 1970s, produced widespread urban chaos, as a series of civic unrests and worker strikes harmed fiscal ratings, real estate values, tourist perceptions and threatened economic opportunities, while urban poverty and interracial conflicts worsened the social fabric of the community, leading to drug addiction and widespread crime (Chan, 2008). The city leadership, mired in large-scale crises, viewed glitzy promotional efforts as 'ancillary, if not irrelevant to their overall strategy of economic development ...' (Greenberg, 2008).

Efforts to refashion New York's image were undertaken in the late 1970's with a slew of public-private tie-ups. Campaigns helped boost local economic growth, and in spite of spasmodic social protests in the form of severely defaced subways, these helped turn around the tarnished label of New York from 'Fear City' to 'The Big Apple' (Chan, 2008). The New York State Department of Commerce launched the 'I Love New York' campaign in 1976, emblematically captured by native New York artist Milton Glaser through the 'I ♥ New York' logo. Image-making mechanisms founded on emotional appeals prompted the restructuring of local political and economic relationships, and with the help of marketers, artists and designers, musical directors and other cultural industry professionals reformed attitudes, shifted real estate values and investor confidence (Greenberg, 2008). The rebranding shifted New York's position into a spanking new commercial and financial hub without the use of large-scale official marketing budgets.

From a triumph of crisis response, not coincidentally, nearly 140 million tourists today flock to the Empire State annually; while, in the ingenious process of commercialising its image, almost 3,000 trademark objections have arisen as the 'I ♥ New York' logo design is openly used, cloned and parodied (Dorsch, 2005). Magazines portray New York City as 'a hip place to live,

work, and shop for young, social climbing urbanites' (Greenberg, 2008), and this image has obviously been lovingly and painstakingly fostered. The strong branding has sustained visitor rates up to the present decade.

Brand Image in Promoting Innovation

Brands attract users beyond traditional consumption. Besides generating commercial and social value in the marketplace, their newly acquired role in modern consumer society today is to contribute to community well-being. The demand for brand images today is to symbolically construct and generate meaning that align with target consumers' own identities (Venkatesh & Meamber, 2006, p.26), paving the way for a competitive playing field, which indirectly promotes innovation. This enhances opportunities for brands, as they must risk innovating and continually develop new products, thus promoting differentiations from one another. As adaptation becomes a key value of nimble brands, companies that own distinctive brand images must strive to provide a range of choices and meet consumer preferences based on an individual's criteria, whether the choice is personal, behavioural or socially motivated. Product development becomes a game of one-upmanship among brand owners, hence, besides serving and satisfying target markets, brands must keep pace and strive to represent an image of excellence, as companies create a virtuous upward spiral of continuous innovation (Lindemann, 2004).

Social responsibility initiatives has arisen in the past two decades to form the basis of brand conversations among consumers, corporations, governments, global agencies, and other stakeholders (Keller, 1993). As discerning users migrate to the Internet, they are keen to scour and share information about brands, 'rather than [hear] what marketers want to say' (Mitchell, 1997, cited in McEnally & de Chernatony 1999, p.18). The era of passive message reception is long over: consumers are proving their energetic involvement in brand creation by comparing user experiences and reviews; enquiring, understanding, and confirming information; tracking competitors and seeking insights, before forming attitudes and views toward the brand.

These pose a tremendous challenge for supply-side marketers, as fractured markets require needs-based market segmentation (Piercy, 1997, cited in McEnally & de Chernatony, p.18). Successful brand designs must factor in long-run survival, and this involves employee engagement programmes (e.g. Shell), corporate social responsibility (McDonalds' local community initiatives), and a greater emphasis on environmental stewardship (e.g. Nike using organic cotton and other environmentally preferred footwear materials: *Nike, Inc.*, n.d.). By expressing its larger social values and mission, an organisation's brand image provides buy-in factors that shape stakeholder perceptions. As increased global warming threatens Earth with wide-scale devastation, sustainability and other environment-related conversations become topical. Brands could catalyse acts of change in terms of its roles and effort to conserve nature's resources. Canvas grocery bags, reusable

food containers, and energy-saving features provide consumers with ethical choices through environmental-friendly packaging and products.

A 2010 study found that 94% of consumers are concerned about the environmental effects of beverage packaging, with 60% Millennials and Gen-Xers willing to pay more for environmentally friendly products (Shayon, 2011). Brown-bagging instead of plastic bags, discounted coffee purchase for tumbler owners, green-tech mobile phones, delivery trucks that run on hybrid systems, petroleum-free soda cans, recyclable merchandise display rack, and organic fashion ranges demonstrate a willing change for Earth's sake. Other strategic branding partnerships with non-governmental organisations enable brands to improve their social responsibility outreach via media and social campaigns, as brand owners supply funds to sustain on-going projects or reach targeted audiences, including rural educational activities, clean water access, medical research, and coordinating donations for victims of calamities.

Estée Lauder's annual breast cancer awareness campaign produced the ubiquitous symbol of breast health, the Pink Ribbon. More than 85 million Pink Ribbons have been distributed worldwide, with millions of dollars raised towards the Breast Cancer Research Foundation (Lauder, n.d). RED is a brand licensed by The Global Fund, which partners corporation such as Nike, Apple Inc., Starbucks, Converse, Gap, Motorola, Dell and others to increase awareness and funding for HIV/AIDS related programmes. Dove's *Campaign for Real Beauty* aims to alter the Western concept of beauty, giving women an esteem boost beyond looking good while staying true to Dove's mission 'to make more women feel beautiful everyday' by narrowing stereotypical views of beauty. The definitive force of Dove's social branding influence for the core message via various advertising and social media platforms has garnered a multi-million viewership and sparked heated global debates (Dove, n.d.), proving how purposeful campaigns for social change via brand identification result in adding value to customer relationships and making a positive impact on stakeholders.

Brand Image in Creating Social Value

Fundamentally, the greatest brand images in the world seek to be social unifiers. Coca-Cola sought to teach the world to sing; Nike celebrates human endeavour; Nokia connects people; Lux soap gives Asian women self-confidence; Budweiser made heroes out of blue-collar workers (Hilton, 2003).

One of the most important keys to lasting consumer relations lies with the emotional benefits offered by the brand. Today's marketplace is awash with a garbled confusion of choices, and understanding the psychological models behind consumers' socialisation processes is a definite asset in contemporary marketing research and practice (Moschis & Smith, 1985).

One approach would be to study the affective connections customers develop and value in brand interactions, and how this determines or potentiates behavioural change in target consumers or social groups. Among the burgeoning, noteworthy trend in brand studies has been the marketing in niche

products and services that reflect individuals' personalities, as well as the successful advertising and promotion of brand personalities via word-of-mouth. For brands to evoke emotional attachments, consumers' values and beliefs take precedence to produce behavioural response, i.e. purchase intention and action (Jacoby & Chestnut, 1978).

Self-expressions, self-definitions and self-presentations are important considerations, and marketers must add on to their portfolio of skills a capacity to unleash the intrinsic and extrinsic values of brands the very same recognised and esteemed by devotees as authentic symbols of the social groups they actually (or aspire to) belong to (McEnally & de Chernatony, 1999, p.16). People react to, and desire, brands that are congruent with their character, using it to express internal attributes; the slogan of brands are promises spoken to effect behavioural and attitudinal response.

Nike encapsulates the emotional character of triumph in its slogan, *Just Do It*, and the use of star athletes in advertising endorsements (Bedbury, 2002). Through a plethora of associations, the product's image moves through altercasting, and projects what it stands for (winning), thereby boosting its innate brand value (McEnally & de Chernatony, 1999, p.30). Aside from promoting sportsmanship, the brand tag deems courage and enjoyment of endeavouring as worthy attributes. Apple's *Think Different* speaks of a constant willingness to innovate, to get away from one's comfort zone, and aim for self-improvement and creativity. Clearly, both these brands inspire people emotionally, arousing their hope to pursue change, thus providing a positive force to accomplish desired results.

Starbucks' brand image revolves around a great coffee experience; quality coffee beans brewed at the right temperature served in plush store environments, setting the tone for java-fuelled enjoyment (Bedbury, 2002). When Guinness ran the *Guinness Irish Pub* giveaway, contestants went all out in poetry writing and pint pulling, steeping into the Irish community's authentic cultural values via the traditional Irish pub environment (Bedbury, 2002: 98-99). Coca-Cola's *The Real Thing* and BMW's *Ultimate Driving Machine* are examples of brand promises that have grown beyond mere slogans, evolving into living icons for the company and their believers (Trout, 2008).

It is a given that humans are emotional beings who constantly need to express themselves, to feel belongingness, and to go in search of others with similar interests in hope of forming, entering, or enlarging their social circles. As people identify others of similar or different socio-economic groups, they recognise social parallels and differences in terms of speech, behaviour, values, or consumption preferences. People with similar taste in music, movies, fashion, love of travel, etc. may converse in insider 'language' forms. Brands which symbolise certain lifestyles like Abercrombie & Fitch, Harley-Davidson, Armani, and others, construct symbolic insights into specific lifestyle behaviours from likes and dislikes, to what keeps them satisfied. A person's habits and behavioural routines are often crucial descriptors of the individual. Chanel perfume, Tag Heuer timepieces, Fender guitars and Nike sneakers affect image and express inner attributes.

The upshot of the search for social approval would be a motivation towards approaching the ideal image, and the tendency would be an image or self-esteem boost through brands in order to alter people's perceptions about them. Elites, to whom social recognition of respectability and self-worth are deemed essential, often recourse to such devices, without which they may perceive indifference of others towards their accomplishments.

Akin to having a trusted circle, research shows consumers choose brands the way we interact with others who are compatible with our attitudes, personality, outlook and views (Aaker, 1996; McEnally & de Chernatony, 1999, p.13, Kotler, 2005, p.71). Brand images allow people to create desires, a crucial force in individual's aspiration for success, where products and services are outlets or mechanisms for self-reward and pampering. Moreover, brand images are symbolic embodiments denoting certain lifestyles and consumption behaviours or preferences. The brand association behind the symbol, design or label suggests belongingness (McEnally & de Chernatony, 1999). Such a socially empowering concept could range from 'sophistication', 'adventurous', 'middle aged', 'eco-friendly' and all their attendant emotional benefits. Abraham Maslow's contribution to humanistic psychology, the *Hierarchy of Needs* was conceptualised to model the basis of his assumption that were motivated by unsatisfied needs.

A core human value is to belong to something larger than us. This desire to belong to a larger group is so deeply embedded in our primal tribal histories that organisations clamber over each other to fill this essential need in targeted customers (Bedbury, 2002). Maslow's *Hierarchy of Needs* describes the sense of belonging and acceptance as a requisite need that must be met before one ascends towards self-esteem and self-actualisation. The stress on notable personal attainments, such as 'social victory', is a fulfilment of our desire for intimate and affectionate relationships (Kunc, 1992).

Images are powerful group identifiers, the social natures of which imbue our family, peers, and neighbours with the same attitudes, values, interests and aspirations. Where loyalty is gained through habitual, emotionally satisfying experiences in consumers' purchase decision (Jacoby & Chestnut, 1978), brand images' could produce causative factors through strong emotional appeals. Social identification via brands connects us tangibly with peers of similar values, interests and aspirations, consumption patterns, tastes etc., and these help aggregate them into certain communities of mutual yet diverse interests. Brands that are symbols of certain lifestyles include Abercrombie & Fitch, Harley-Davidson, Armani, Louis Vuitton, Quiksilver, Roxy, Billabong, Mini Cooper, Starbucks, etc.

Brands could analyse these social relationships to interpret 'connectedness' using the design emotion model; that is, by complementing the emotional dimension with every point of communication in the consumer interaction chain (Pullman & Gross, 2004). Examples include brand image expression of safety and security (Volvo), freedom (Harley Davidson), adventure and youth culture (Red Bull), etc.

Loyalty helps brands achieve income returns and economic goals by being unique and distinctive, but this should not be at the expense of being cheap (Light, 1994). Revenue growth is a direct result of nurturing strategic customer relationships (Kotler, 2005, p.101), and this rests on the image of service reliability, quality and assurance, brand evangelising through word-of-mouth, or evaluation of user experiences among peers and acquaintances. For brands with strong equity such as high recognition or preference, customers are willing to pay higher prices just to get the product even if this comes at a loss (Reichheld, 1993). Loyalty becomes a habitual act in consumer interaction across espoused personal values, beliefs, social, or cultural norms, symbolising the positive, superior or competitive attributes of the brand image for the consumer that produces product involvement (Hanzaee et al., 2011).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study involved a survey of urban adults, aged between 18-27 years. A simple random sampling method was used, and a total of 120 participants were given a timeframe of 45 days to respond, in the survey conducted online from mid-May to the end of June 2013. Respondents comprised employed professionals, executives, and managers, as well as self-employed individuals and students, providing internet access regardless of their location within Malaysia.

Research Instrument

To evaluate respondent perceptions and awareness about brands and the effects of brand images, a structured online questionnaire was designed and distributed via <https://docs.google.com/>. This method enabled the researcher to analyse and note overall respondents' enjoyment and awareness of brand images, and how they evaluated the effectiveness and capacity of the brands in their consumption. The late adolescent and young adult age segment was chosen due to the greater exposures to media influences for respective segments, enabling them to examine and elicit responses which demonstrate their critical awareness of brands.

A series of relevant brand image-related questions were asked in attempt to analyse, record and interpret data related to the respondents' attitudes, behaviours and perceptions towards brands. From the total 120 returned questionnaires, data was collated and studied to determine the relevance, salience, and the significance of the brand image to their self-expression, personal experiences, views, and social values in consumption. Due consideration was given to ensure cultural relevance of questions to the Malaysian background.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The data produced from the study shows brand preference and attitudes were correlated to consumption decisions that

Do you buy only reputable products with a positive image?

Pie Chart 1

Would you agree that the use of familiar brand images has improved your personal confidence and overall wellbeing?

Pie Chart 4

Do you agree brand image can influence customer loyalty on any particular brand?

Pie Chart 2

Would you agree that brands play a role in the improvement of the economy and living standards in countries?

Pie Chart 5

Would you agree that inspiring brand images and slogans play a role to affect your feelings, beliefs, opinions and decisions?

Pie Chart 3

Would you agree that brand images are a form of motivator that encourage you to achieve your goal/s?

Pie Chart 6

gave insight on participants' levels of brand awareness, and emotional benefits gained from individual and collective engagement with brands.

Pie Chart 1 shows that 68% buy products perceived as 'reputable' from association with its positive image. Pie Chart 2 reveals that 90 out of 120 people, or 75%, think that brand images may influence consumer brand loyalty.

Pie Chart 3 shows 55% of respondents benefited emotionally from the slogan of brands, agreeing on the role of brand identities in shaping their emotions. Pie Chart 4 shows only 10%, or 12 respondents, did not believe branded products could improve their confidence or wellbeing.

Pie Chart 5 shows 72, or 60%, are aware that brands contribute to the world economy with living standards; 40% of respondents think that brands are not deemed functional or important assets that enhance a country's economic position. Pie Chart 6 shows that 85%, or 102 out of 120 participants, are motivated by specific brand images to attain their desired goals. In this study, the findings found that consumers' brand

awareness has extended beyond quality and price-conscious purchasing. Brand relationships exist in positive and beneficial ways, and are salient to consumers' personal and social perspectives, besides influencing their consumption preferences and improving the value they seek in social interactions with others.

Among the varied factors that created customer loyalty, *Visual Experience* gained 36 votes, followed by *Quality*, which received 30 votes. *Price* and *Advertisement* received an equal vote of 18 each, and *Packaging* scored 12 votes. A little over half the respondents agreed that brand images have helped express or define their personalities or in gaining status or respect; others were not really concerned about the brand image aspect, which infers that pricing, performance and quality were more important drivers.

108 out of 120 respondents agree that possessing branded products boosted their confidence. With current social pressures, individuals wishing to avoid social rejection or humiliation find branded goods and their identifiers useful in reckoning

stature upgrade and social confidence. Quality products appeal to their rational consumption motives, but brands reflect their social status as informed consumers with socially approved good taste. 72 respondents affirmed that brands' play a role in raising living standards of countries in some ways, and brand images are valuable motivators that poise them for further social successes and challenges. Consumption of well-placed brands enable them to plan purchases ahead in order to obtain the product or service desired, while some used brands as a form of enjoyment, for self-reward or pampering purposes.

SUGGESTIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

Research shows that brand personalities contribute to the growth of local economies, giving a social and affective dimension to individuals' consumption experience (Aaker, 1996; McEnally & de Chernatony 1999). This study found a strong correlation between Malaysian consumers' awareness via brand image engagement and their personal and social perspectives. Just *how much* brand images influence consumption preferences or their engagement with others in social conversations is an untapped area of research. It is evident upon close analysis of data from this survey that consumers today demand more than quality in brand experiences. Social experiences can produce brand encounters, and research can improve understanding of the salience of brands' emotional linkages which transcend company attributes, logo design, or trademark recognition (Pallotta, 2011).

The lack of impactful of local studies on consumer perceptions is the single-most important factor to urge on brand marketing research initiatives; hence, future research could affect the cultivation of brands' social value, and therefore the potential of this relationship should be further field-tested. Greater exchange platforms will require greater industry and scholarly knowledge sharing among advertising and media experts and marketing managers, and these could discuss social branding themes such as the role of social connections in building brand loyalty; and brands which spur a constant search for personal achievement or to exceed social expectations. Most retailers understand the need to connect emotionally with consumers; yet, a good many do not know how (or are not trying to) put principle into practice, neglecting the social and emotional valuation in lieu of low price promises, which appeal to customers' sense of reason, but eschews their passions (Berry, 2001). Another notable implication from this study is that brand image reputation, along with consumers' positive brand experiences and aspirational motives are signs of brands' approachability. Future studies could contemplate factors, which boost brand equity and brands' potential to set a price premium over the cost of provision, thus increasing willingness to purchase. Quantitative studies could be replicated in non-urban segments to evaluate whether price, performance, quality and desire for value comes with the proviso of socially-responsible merchants that bear positive brand identities.

CONCLUSION

Society today is daily educated to recognise the importance of brands. Brand management essentially, the process of constructing, developing and sustaining brands has evolved from the bricolage of artifices of past practice; generating designs, images, labels, slogans, etc., and continues erratically today to produce a new vision of organisational identity where ingrained cultural values clash mightily, 'spontaneously and stochastically' (Massi & Harrison, 2008, p.4) with the aesthetics of postmodern values and the pastiche of new media simulated realities and hyper-reality tools (Massi & Harrison, 2008, p.3). Brands draw us into wider discursive implications that are at once social, political, economic, and moral in nature. Our conception of purpose, profit and passions can be promptly analysed from what we spend on social goods (Hilton, 2003). To boost fairer economic goals in the midst of widening inequality, brands must be couched as sustainable symbols, delivering both quantifiable and immeasurable benefits to their target publics, whilst being malleable, transforming and moving to integrate shifts in our emotional and values spectra.

Stakeholders demand new consumer standards to be met in a range of ways: re-examination of corporation ethics and brands' contributions to the economy and living standards; continuous social innovation to improve brand value and competitive positioning through consumer advocacy; assessing and managing global business opportunities to strengthen brand equity and improve perceptions of what unique brands stand for (Aaker, 1991; Hall, 1999; Lindemann, 2004). By summing up a company's best and worst experiences, brand images represent a raft of associated aspects linking attitudes, emotions, and motivational appeals to consumption behaviour, and these are the cumulative outcomes of brand interactions. This will be a fundamental attribute for businesses steering their brands to further heights, as valuable social conversations with staunch consumers inspire the latter to continue being part of the brand-making process.

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FEEDING YOUR PIGGY BANK WITH INTENTIONS: A STUDY ON SAVING BEHAVIOUR, SAVING STRATEGIES, AND HAPPINESS

Santiago De Francisco Vela, Mafalda Casais, Pieter Desmet
Delft University of Technology
Delft Institute of Positive Design
✉ defrancisco.san@gmail.com, m.casais@tudelft.nl, p.m.a.desmet@tudelft.nl

ABSTRACT

The act of saving money can connect one's present state to a meaningful future state, especially if we consider money not as a direct source of happiness, but as a resource for engaging in meaningful activities. To explore how design can contribute to making the act of saving more meaningful, we conducted two studies. The first consisted of questionnaires and interviews about saving. The second was a study on the BILLEGAS piggy bank design case, in which we sought to determine success factors, and evaluate them among three groups in different levels, during a four-week period. The study indicated that design could stimulate empathy with the product, a meaningful saving experience with a relevant contribution to well-being, and an increase in the amount of money saved. The study culminated with new insights to enrich the meaningfulness of the saving experience in other contexts, and to increase the user's well-being.

KEY WORDS: *Positive Design, saving behaviour, happiness, ownership, attachment*

INTRODUCTION

It's often said that 'money can't buy happiness', expressing the idea that rich people are not necessarily happier than those who are poor. Even though this is 'just a saying', it is supported by recent findings of researchers who study the relationship between happiness and financial resources (for an overview, see Biswas-Diener, 2008). Once people have sufficient financial resources to survive, their happiness does not rely on the amount of additional money, but rather on *how* they spend their money (Dunn & Norton, 2013). Some authors have proposed that 40% of people's happiness relies on the activities they do, and only 10% on circumstances like wealth, weather, or location (Lyubomirsky et al., 2005; Lyubomirsky, 2008). However, even if money may not be a direct source of happiness, it can still be considered a *resource* that enables people to engage in meaningful activities, therefore making a salient contribution to their happiness. We therefore propose that it is interesting to consider the well-being effects of saving. Saving is understood as an activity in which an individual accumulates money with the intent to spend it in the future. Given that saving can connect one's present state to a meaningful future

state, we became interested in exploring how this behaviour can be experienced as more meaningful, and in that sense contribute to well-being. We used the BILLEGAS piggy bank as a design case in order to distinguish and evaluate factors that could enhance the act of saving and make it meaningful. BILLEGAS is a collection of money boxes depicting cartoon characters that allows the users to choose a character, pick a name for it, and set a saving intention. In doing so, it adds a tangible quality to one's intangible saving intentions. Despite the fact that this product was not designed with the specific intent of making a contribution to happiness, it incorporates some basic ideas that make saving enjoyable as well as effective, and in this sense we found it interesting to explore regarding meaning and empathy.

MONEY AND HAPPINESS

The degree to which economic matters influence quality of life, and therefore happiness, has been studied extensively (e.g. Veenhoven, 2000). Issues like income, GDP, and accumulated wealth are found to have little impact on individual happiness

(Hagerty & Veenhoven, 2003), unlike circumstances such as weather (Rehdanz & Maddison, 2005), or behaviours like cultivating positive relationships (Ryff & Singer, 2006; Lyubomirsky & Kurtz, 2011; Seligman, 2011). Dunn and Norton (2013) studied the increase of happiness through the spending of money in a meaningful way, and have identified five important strategies in which spending money can contribute to happiness. The strategies they identified were to buy experiences, to make it a treat, to pay now and consume later, to buy time, and to invest in others. There are two main hypotheses behind these strategies. The first is the contribution of social interaction and how people share and help others, and the second the contribution of positive expectation and the surprise effect. Even though Dunn and Norton focused on spending behaviour, we propose that their insights on social connections, on the power of intentions, and on experiential purchases, can be applied to saving. Indeed, these authors also acknowledged the importance of saving in relation to well-being, stating that saving makes a direct contribution to happiness.

Money is an enabler of personal and social activities that can contribute to our subjective well-being (Dunn & Norton, 2013), and saving can be seen as a preventive experience: saving prevents negative emotions by supporting the individual in building positive traits and having positive subjective experiences (Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi, 2000). This is accomplished by the act of defining intentions that let people commit to a goal. The motivation to save money is still rarely explored and so is its relation with happiness. Furthermore, the formats in which people can save money, like saving accounts, piggy banks, or other investing strategies, have been hitherto insufficiently explored in a design (and well-being) perspective. We aim to understand how design can motivate people to save money in a more meaningful way and contribute to their happiness.

DESIGN AND HAPPINESS

Based on the knowledge gathered in the field of Positive Psychology, a Positive Design approach proposes that design can contribute to the happiness of individuals and society. Desmet and Pohlmeier (2013) describe the three basic ingredients to stimulate human flourishing through design. The first one is Design for Pleasure, related to the enjoyment of the moment; the second is Design for Personal Significance, related to a sense of personal meaning derived from the pursuit of meaningful goals; the third is Design for Virtue, related to the moral quality in one's interactions with the world.

The design case used in this study is a simple money box called BILLEGAS. The first step is to select a character (eight characters are available). Next, the user names the piggy bank and sets his or her intention for saving. This information is written on the bottom of each box, along with the starting date of the saving period. Once this is done, the user can start saving and can decide, according to the intention or the starting date when he or she wants to open it. By writing it on the box, the user makes the name and the saving intention more concrete and easier to revisit.

The BILLEGAS was designed to help people improve their saving experience. We used the Positive Design framework to evaluate characteristics of these piggy banks based on the three ingredients that compose it: the playfulness of interaction (Pleasure), the act of writing down an intention (Personal Significance), and the commitment to that intention (Virtue). The playfulness of interaction (including selecting a character, customizing, and naming the product) will help users to enjoy their saving activity. The act of writing down one's intentions and displaying the product in a visible place will help users to experience the meaningfulness of their saving activity, making the mental connection between the saving, and the meaningful activity which will be made possible with the saved money. Finally, it relates to virtue in the sense that users set intentions, which translate into commitments that nudge them into considering their spending and saving behaviours in a more careful and responsible way. In order to understand better the value of the characteristics of this product in terms of fostering well-being, it is interesting to evaluate it in a real context. For that we carried out a study to determine the impact of this particular piggy bank on people's happiness.

'HAPPY SAVINGS' STUDIES

The aim of this research was to explore if and how design can contribute to the meaningfulness of saving money. In order to do that, two studies were conducted based on the BILLEGAS. The aim of Study one (including two questionnaires and in-depth interviews) was to increase our general understanding of saving behaviour and identify the factors that enhance and give meaning to the saving experience used in the BILLEGAS piggy bank. The results were used in Study two, in which participants were instructed to save money for a period of four weeks. The aim of Study two was to validate design strategies that resulted from Study one, and identify new opportunities to enrich this experience. Participants were split into three groups: a control group with blank piggy bank boxes (1), a group that used the current version of the BILLEGAS (2), and a group that used a customized version of the BILLEGAS (3).

Study One: Questionnaires and interviews

In Study one, two questionnaires were administered; one that focused on saving in general, and one that focused on the use of the BILLEGAS. The aim of the first questionnaire was to increase our understanding of how many people save money, the variety of saving methods, advantages and disadvantages of saving, and motivations for both long-term and short-term saving. The aim of the second questionnaire was to determine which elements of the BILLEGAS piggy bank were considered to have the biggest effect on meaningfulness. In addition to the two questionnaires, three in-depth interviews were done with BILLEGAS users. In those interviews, we inquired about the use, concept, look, and meaning of the product. Furthermore, we discussed the kind of relationships that users develop with their piggy banks.

The first questionnaire was distributed through social media networks. In total, 83 people responded, from 29 different countries (35 females and 48 males), with an age range between 21 and 46 years. Among this group 58% were students. The second questionnaire was distributed on the BILLEGAS Facebook fan page, and was sent to people who had recently acquired the product. In total 23 people responded (13 females and 10 males) from different regions of Colombia, the country where the product originated. From the respondents, 70% were employed or freelancers, while 27% were students. From the people that filled in the second questionnaire, three people were willing to participate in an in-depth interview about the use of the BILLEGAS. The interview was set up as a semi-structured interview with the main purpose of identifying the elements that motivated the users to resort to this piggy bank. The interview was structured in three main parts: previous saving experiences, experiences with the BILLEGAS piggy bank, and the relation between money, saving, and happiness.

Results of Study One

First Questionnaire

The majority of the respondents saved money (90%) and considered saving important, which is in line with findings from previous studies (e.g. Furnham, 1999; Xiao et al., 2008). Of these savers, 69% used saving accounts, and 10% used piggy banks. Most respondents (38%), reported to have undefined intentions (UI) for saving money ‘...to be certain that I have some money in case of an emergency’; 28% mentioned defined short-term intentions (DSTI) ‘...for a pair of sneakers or a concert’; 23% mentioned defined long-term intentions (DLTI) ‘...saving up for moving, for having a family, maybe getting a car, traveling, etc.’ Figure 1 presents a word cloud to give an impression of the most stated intentions. From these answers we defined three lists of intentions, which later were used as a reference in the second study (see Table 1).

Figure 1. Word cloud of intentions according to the questionnaire answers

SHORT TERM INTENTIONS	LONG TERM INTENTIONS	UNDEFINED INTENTIONS
Time with friends	House/real estate	Having money
Time with family	Traveling/big trip	Unexpected needs
Gifts for others	Transport (car, motorcycle, boat...)	Future
Pampering	Cosmetic surgery	Peace of mind
Clothes/shoes/ accessories	Study	Help friends/family
Domestic appliances	Loans/debts	Charity
Personal electronic devices	Get settled	Safety
Get away weekend/small trip	Building a business	Investment
Hobbies/sport	Pension	Build a life/family
Furniture/ decoration	Holiday house	Freedom
Fixing/renovations		Independence
Events		Stability
Buy stuff for others		Health/illness
Small investments		Maintenance
Special meals		Emergency
New experiences		Legal issues/ unemployment
Getting a pet		
Small transport (skate, bike...)		

Table 1. List of intentions resulting from the questionnaire answers

Out of the respondents, 67% affirmed it was important to have knowledge about saving strategies; 58% said it was important to learn about saving; and 43% claimed it was important to teach about saving. The statement that money makes people happy was deemed unimportant by 40% of the respondents; while 43% said it was important. Regarding money’s ability to help people accomplish their goals, 69% agreed. And finally 64% of the respondents said money is important in their lives.

Second Questionnaire

49% of the respondents said they saved money in savings accounts, however, some of them mentioned their experience as

unsatisfying. Regarding the BILLEGAS, 50% said they used it to save money, and 47% for decoration. When asked about the different qualities of the BILLEGAS, 67% said the possibility to write down the saving intention was important, while 19% said it was mandatory. Furthermore, the act of planning the savings was deemed important by 67% and mandatory by 29%. The respondents said that the BILLEGAS has helped them to save moderately (67%), and a lot (19%).

In-Depth interviews

Interviewees talked about the importance of saving in previous experiences 'besides my piggy bank (...) I have a saving account, escrow account and TDC [term deposit certificates]'; experience with the BILLEGAS 'she helped me a lot to be more committed [...] every time I see him, I remember that I have to put a bill inside'; the importance of the BILLEGAS characteristics (name, intention, and date) 'naming it and setting the intention makes it more personal... when you get involved with the intention it turns out to be more interesting [...] naming the BILLEGAS was important because we were calling her by her name: Paris. We were saying "We have to take the money to feed Paris"... so she turned into a character of the house, during that time she was alive'; and the importance of saving and its relation with happiness 'saving is in the process of being happy, I don't see it as an end. I see it as the process of saving continuously for a period of time that satisfies me. Then the whole process turns into my happiness'.

Conclusions of Study One

From Study one we learnt three things. The first one is that people perceived saving as an activity that can contribute to their goals and achievements. A study about the saving habit of young people demonstrated that saving was a very important habit (Furnham, 1999) and that it can contribute to one's life satisfaction (Xiao et al., 2008). Secondly, there is a higher chance to commit to an intention, when it is established and written before starting to save. And lastly, customizing the piggy banks develops a level of attachment which increases the motivation to save. We used these insights to structure Study two, in which we wanted to evaluate certain characteristics at different levels and determine which ones contribute to happiness and how.

Study two: Saving experiment

Study two started with an introduction session, in which twelve participants received a 'saving kit' to save for a four-week period, and ended with a creative group session to discuss the experience. For this study, twelve participants were recruited, and randomly split into three groups, which were each given different piggy bank styles. Group one (the control group) was given a blank piggy bank. Group two had the option to choose one of four available BILLEGAS characters (there was no direct customization besides this choice), and was instructed to name the character, and set a saving intention. Group three had a customizable version of a BILLEGAS character which was a basic female or male character that could be customized with stickers, ranging through an assortment of eyes, accessories,

and logos for the character's clothes. They were instructed to name their characters and set up a saving intention.

Respondents in all three groups were asked to save for a period of four weeks, meanwhile keeping track of their motivation and thoughts about saving in a diary booklet. The booklet was divided into weeks and each week had a topic for the participants to think and reflect upon, as well as a calendar to record any situation or emotion that contributed to happiness during that period. The first week was about intentions, goals, and achievements. The second week was about happiness and its importance to keep up motivation. The third week was about savings, strategies, methods, and stories. And lastly, the fourth week was about reflection, assessment, and learning. In the fourth week the participants were also asked to take a picture of their piggy bank in the context where they had it.

During the creative follow-up sessions (each group had a separate session), the groups engaged in five exercises to catalyse a discussion about their experiences. In the first exercise, participants were asked to choose from a pool of activities representing the different saving intentions (Table 1), and placed them in a target, where the area closer to the centre would be for the ones most relevant to their happiness. For the second exercise the participants were handed six blank papers to expand on different themes: personal sphere, relationship sphere, social sphere, professional sphere, global sphere, and spiritual sphere. These exercises aimed to provide a thoughtful exploration of the participants' priorities in various aspects of their lives (which can influence decisions and intentions for saving). For the third exercise the participants were asked to pull out discussion cards containing different debate questions. In the fourth exercise the participants were handed a self-assessment sheet with several steps to evaluate and reflect on the experience of saving with the BILLEGAS. It asked them to take a photo with the piggy bank, to review their saving intention, and to state things that were done to pursue it. Furthermore, the exercise asked for a mood evaluation and an assessment of how close they were to the intention, followed by an explanation, and prospects on the continuation of saving. For the final exercise, a discussion about the role of technology, customization, and the responsibility of banks was raised among the groups.

Results of Study Two

The results from the booklets served mostly as input for the sessions, which were used to draw new possible directions towards meaningful saving.

Exercise One: Saving intentions

In group one the undefined intentions (UI) and defined short-term intentions (DSTI) were selected as most relevant. The participants agreed that unexpected emergencies or unpredicted future situations (UI) and special activities that involved social interactions (DSTI) motivated them to save. For group two, the defined long-term intentions (DLTI), which were activities that needed more time and effort, were considered the most

important. As for group three, the most relevant intentions were also future oriented, as group two, however, they also stated the importance of DSTI as motivators to save. Although no particular pattern was observed, all groups agreed that defined intentions are motivating to save for, and undefined ones are mostly necessary to save for.

Exercise Two: Spheres of Happiness

Results from this exercise showed that all participants, disregarding the groups, were tuned into aspects related to their relationships (interpersonal connections, in which participants mentioned *togetherness, love, trust, honesty, learning from others, and giving support*); professional status (occupation, and the participants mentioned *challenges, accomplishments, success, and development* as contributing to happiness, but also *income and financial stability*); and spirituality (believes and practices, and for this the participants indicated *peace of mind, connection, nature, and spiritual growth*). The latter is important, taking into account that participants have different backgrounds and different religions. For the remaining spheres there were no connections found. However, participants from group two and three were tuned regarding the personal (inner-self, and the answers mentioned different topics like *freedom, peace, balance, education and health*); and social spheres (collective society, and the mentioned topics related to it were *being aware, sharing, communicating, supporting, and helping at community level*). This connection can be derived from the relation of setting up an intention.

Exercise Three: Discussion cards

Results on this exercise showed that visual reminders (written intention or personification of the goal) help to encourage and motivate the savings 'When I used to open the drawer of my office and I saw this guy [the piggy bank], he was reminding me: "Hey you haven't saved!" So I put money in it'. Also, setting up rules and creating a habit are strategies that can help with saving: 'Saving is about rules: The spare money that I have I put it in the piggy bank, and for me it is sacred, nobody touches it'. Saving is perceived as buffer activity (Dunn & Norton, 2013) 'Saving gives you a feeling of safety... whenever I picture my future I want to feel safe'. The exercise also showed the importance of identifying and prioritizing intentions in contributing towards meaningful saving: 'Having a clear goal, and knowing that you can make someone happy with it'.

Exercise Four: Self-assessment sheet

The results of the self-assessment sheet showed that the motivation in group one was not very high, and the savings were also not particularly high. In the self-assessment sheet, the participants of group one placed themselves far from the goal. In group two and three there was a better outcome, and particularly in group three the results were outstanding. Due to the relationship that was built with the characters, the participants of group three were able to gather considerable amounts of money, but also described the saving experience with great joy.

Exercise Five: Final discussion

Participants reflected upon the topics mentioned above and gave insights into how they envisioned the act of saving in the future 'It would be nice to have some sort of service that allows you to put money in it, but not touching it... like having a kind of reward or a visual cue for your progress... you have saved till here, but if you put in more then you can get this or that'.

REFLECTION ON FINDINGS

In this section of the paper we reflect on the learned lessons about effectiveness and meaningfulness in saving. During study two we were able to find relevant connections between the elements we were evaluating and how they improved the saving experience. However, there were new important insights learned from the study that are potentially applicable in real-life contexts of saving. The use of the piggy bank was described as being evocative of the act of saving, like a tangible reminder. The currently available saving solutions, according to the participants, lack an evocative visual quality that reminds users to save, and shows them how much they have saved, or how much to save. According to the participants, it is this visual quality that stimulates a constant motivation. One participant of group two described how the visual appeal of the animal character he chose provoked a reaction that extended to his friends, making them feel the need to 'feed the penguin'. This engagement became even more evident in the group that customized their own characters in the form of a self-portrait or caricature (group three), naming them with their own names or nicknames 'it has so much similar appearance with me, also has my nick name'. This suggested to the participants that they had to take care of, as they put it, 'a better you' or 'a friend'. In the study, we found that the level of attachment and the power of customization strengthen the relation with the piggy bank, making it more meaningful to save. According to Beggan (1992), when a person owns an object, it is linked to them as a self-extension. The characterization of the piggy banks in group three made the participants treat them in a special way, and added symbolic value by becoming an extended part of them (Belk, 1988). Some participants engaged in dialogue with the customized piggy banks, and some put them in special places to be able to look at them: 'I liked her. I even talked to her when putting money in'. Identity and self-expression reinforce the sense of self, making symbolic possessions, which represent the self or attachments to others, to have high weights on positive emotions (Richins, 1994). To introduce an avatar in a virtual format of saving could be a strategy to increase engagement and meaningfulness, as well as motivation for saving '...it makes it personal, so I'm giving money to myself, and I think it's funny'.

Participants proposed that having a list of saving intentions (suggested by the hosting institutions) could help users to review their own priorities and goals when saving. Prior studies on saving (e.g. Furnham, 1999) have shown that people save money when they want something special, which can be understood as a goal. A goal is a cognitive representation of a desired

endpoint that impacts evaluations, emotions, and behaviours (Fishbach & Ferguson, 2007). The control group in the study (group one), unlike the other groups, did not receive instructions to set an intention, and turned out to be less motivated to save than the remaining groups. In that sense, the setting of saving intentions can be seen as a contribution of this study to a real-life context of saving.

From study two we learned that in order to make saving meaningful it was important to have a method to keep track of motivation, thoughts, and progress on savings, expenses, and goals. Such features could benefit a digital format, making it more relatable and meaningful, and could be implemented, for example, as a mobile phone application.

The participants in the study also discussed rewards. In case of small rewards like interests in saving accounts, the suggestions were that they be announced or made visual, to increase motivation. They also mentioned the idea of a wish list in association with the act of saving that would aid the visualization of the amounts saved. For example, a user would set up an inspirational list of products, travels, or activities (e.g. education). When the user reached a certain amount, it would be visualized as elements of the list, for example 'you have saved enough for/ to buy X'. Other amounts could also be used, for example related to helping others 'you have saved the equal of one child's education costs in X country'. This ability to transform currency into something significant allows for an 'applied' form of visualization, and such a solution could potentially increase effectiveness of saving by means of a virtuous incentive.

The use of gamification in savings could improve the experience by promoting an experiential engagement, for example, by letting users set up their own rules that would ensure more control over the saving process, but also a self-challenge, in a virtue oriented approach.

In regards to the current formats of saving, the participants stated that since most of them use debit or credit cards, it was difficult to save cash money, but also the use of this system was a misrepresented way to deal with money, since it lost its tangibility. The participants suggested a solution of hybrid props in replacement of the card as an alternative that would offer more relatedness, and thus a bigger notion of awareness and consequence when dealing with money, contributing to a more meaningful and less abstract relation when saving and spending money.

CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER DEVELOPMENTS

From the studies we conclude that design can contribute to the meaningfulness of saving, by enabling users to set up an intention, visualize it, and empathize with it. During the studies, participants mentioned several occasions in which the use of money is now being limited to credit and debit cards, instead of coins and bills. We see this as a tendency that can increase with new technological developments. However, it is possible to learn a lot from traditional ways of saving, and such lessons that can provide a salient contribution to well-being. The evaluated strategies are seen as potential enhancers of meaningfulness in

saving and thus contribute to the happiness of those engaged in saving. In addition, new insights were gathered in other areas to increase meaningfulness in saving: the first one was the ability to choose and transform currency into more meaningful references by visualizing the progress of savings; secondly, the use of alternative, more relatable forms, of handling and saving money by resembling the use of the piggy bank combined with digital services; and lastly, the sense of community as a support for shared saving intentions, creating saving networks.

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DEMAND RESPONSIVE TRANSPORT AS A SOCIAL INNOVATION

THE CASE OF SKEWIEL MOBIEL

H. (Rick) Schotman and G.D.S. (Geke) Ludden
University of Twente
✉ h.schotman@utwente.nl, g.d.s.ludden@utwente.nl

ABSTRACT

People are increasingly growing older. Growing older is likely to come with, for example, decreasing mobility and therefore increasing dependency. This can reduce the social connectedness of older people. As an effect, a social challenge is growing: loneliness.

In response to this challenge, local governments offer mobility services that the elderly can use to go out. However, from our test bed of a mobility product-service system for seniors, we learned that many such services focus too much on transporting people from A to B, while the user experience of the service leaves room for improvement. In this paper we discuss how a demand responsive transport system, set-up as a social innovation, improves social connectedness, instead of delivering mobility alone. We found that the service itself provides social satisfaction, and that the service was not necessarily used for social activities. Rather, the service was used for activities of daily life.

KEYWORDS: *Seniors, Mobility, Social Connectedness, Product-service system, Social Innovation*

INTRODUCTION

Aging is a worldwide trend, especially in the more developed regions (United Nations, 2012), that results in various societal challenges that relate to topics such as housing, health-care, and mobility. Increasing life expectancy, and therefore increasing use of healthcare and other facilities have resulted in financial threats that need to be dealt with.

A solution that is often advocated, is to let people live healthier and longer independently. Being mobile is a crucial factor for an independent and healthy ageing population. Inescapably, when people grow older, their mobility decreases. For example, they have to stop driving a car or cannot ride a bike anymore. As a result, independency to move freely reduces, while dependency on others grows.

Next to ageing, the western society has reached an era of urbanization. Urbanization results in the depopulation of rural areas, and facilities such as banks, medical facilities, or supermarkets, disappear due to a decreasing number of clients. As a consequence, rural areas transform from functional communities to purely residential areas (Simon, 2004). This development results in rural dwellers becoming even more dependent on mobility means to be able to continue

using these facilities. Seniors mostly stay in rural areas, or move to rural areas (Kullberg, 2002), and they can become especially affected by this development. The combination of decreasing mobility and disappearing facilities can result in seniors that become homebound. Public transport is seen as an alternative to keep seniors from solitude, but access to public transport in rural areas is low compared to the city, and has been decreasing (Harms, 2008). Moreover, Jorritsma and Olde Kalter (2008) found that seniors are not a substantial group of public transport users and discounts do not have a significant effect on bus use among elderly.

So, it seems that public transport is of limited use to counter loneliness and to maintain or improve social connectedness. Demand responsive transport (DRT) is regarded as the next possible solution. Nelson et al. (2010), found that the goal of DRT systems is to increase social connectedness for people who suffer reduced mobility, whether it is from impairment, or from infrastructural reasons.

In this paper, we will focus on how DRT services aim at helping people to live independently, and what impact DRT use has on social connectedness. We will first look at a number of international demand responsive systems (DRTs) and consider how such systems are defined, what role they play in

people's lives and how we can interpret such systems from a socially innovative perspective.

Next, we will consider how DRT systems connect to independent living and daily activities and we will introduce Skewiel Mobiel, a test bed, which we consider to be an innovative, and very socially defined DRT service. We will interpret the results conducted from our test bed, which we obtained through semi-structured interviews with users, open interviews with drivers, and a quantitative trip analysis, spanning fourteen months. As a conclusion, we found that Skewiel Mobiel offers an experience that is very close to the experience of living life in an ordinary way. By this, Skewiel Mobiel shows what a DRT can look like if it is based on social innovation principles.

SOCIAL INNOVATION

Many definitions for social innovations exist. We follow Harris and Albury (2009), who propose to describe social innovation as “innovation explicitly for the social and public good”. They argue that social innovation is used for social challenges that are “neglected by traditional forms of private market provision and which have often been poorly served or unresolved by services organised by the state” (2009, p.16).

Because social innovation is based on social challenges, it is not defined by addressing and implementing new products, but by the aim to solve social challenges. This can result in very innovative services that are based on ‘old’ technology.

Christensen et al. (2006) state that catalytic innovations should be used to solve social problems. They wrote on catalytic innovations for social change and describe the problem of organizations that spend many resources on maintaining and optimizing their service for their current clients, but neglect the group of people that need basic services. Hereby, a status quo appears and innovation is not stimulated. The premise of Christensen et al. (2006) is that status-quo should be disrupted and need to disappear. As a consequence, they believe that social innovation cannot start with optimizing current processes, because that would sustain the status quo. Instead, they argue that social innovation is about more efficient solutions, instead of higher quality products. Moreover, they argue that new, disruptive solutions, “are likely to come from outside the ranks of the established players”, and that the new solution should be ‘good enough’ (Christensen et al., 2006, p.2) formulated guidelines for good catalytic innovations, which should:

- Be low-cost and simple alternatives for over-served, underserved, or ignored customers;
- Focus on the solution, rather than the organization, and it has to ‘meet a significant underserved need’. The solutions must be considered ‘good enough’ by users;
- Have a business model that is able to introduce, scale-up, replicate, and sustain the innovation.

Peerby (‘Peerby. Borrow the things you need from people in your neighborhood,’ n.d.) and Shareyourmeal (‘Shareyourmeal.net, what’s your neighbor cooking?’, n.d.) are good examples of social catalytic innovations. Both are sharing platforms where people can share their tools and seldom-used products (Peerby), or prepared meals (Shareyourmeal) with their neighbours. The organizations are new entrants in their respective service segments (tool renting and food delivery services) and both organizational forms are successful, but simple online communities. For Peerby, the offered products are almost by definition not brand new or very high-end, but the power of Peerby is to have a simple service that provides all kinds of products good enough for temporary activities.

Shareyourmeal is not about the highest quality meal, the most nutritious, or the fanciest possible. Shareyourmeal’s power is as a simple service that provides access to meals that are home-cooked with personal attention, and which offer a huge variety for a reasonable price in a local setting.

In this paper, we focus on the mobility services segment, and on DRT systems in particular, and we will show that in this area a lot can be learned from social innovation theory.

DEMAND RESPONSIVE TRANSPORT SYSTEMS

Over the last decades, many local governments, as well as third parties, have initiated new mobility services that work as DRT or flexible transit service (FTS). These small-scale services offer transport to people who cannot use regular mobility means, such as a private car or a bike. Also, it is intended for people who have no access to public transport, due to the lack of transport connections in the area (such as bus stops or train stations), or due to physical barriers that result in not being able to reach a transport connection. Many services fill the gap that disappearing public transport leaves behind and connect with it. By this, such services are intended to address the social issue of safeguarding social connectedness for this group.

Compared to regular public transport, DRT services are more effective ways of transport, because they generally do not need to have fixed schedules or fixed stops. They go when they are needed. Advanced flexible systems have more similarities with taxi-based transport and offer the same door-to-door mobility. Sloman and Hendy (2008) give an overview of various DRT services and FTS systems, such as TreinTaxi and Regiotaxi in The Netherlands, PubliCar in Switzerland, Taxi-Tub in France and Anruf Sammel Taxis in Germany. Moreover, they introduce a number of UK-based DRTs, but they see UK systems as less advanced systems, as they usually have fixed routes or fixed stops, whereas the mainland Europe-based services are more flexible.

Many DRT systems start as a transport service for specific target groups, such as elderly or disabled. However, the more mature the service becomes, the more target groups are added until it becomes an open-access service.

Figure 1: Development of demand responsiveness of DRT services. Source: Brake et al. (2006)

Most systems are run by traditional taxi firms or settled transport service providers. For instance, RegioTaxi in The Netherlands is assigned to taxi companies through competitive tenders, and TreinTaxi is run by the Dutch Railways and the Swiss PubliCar by PostBus; the national mail and passenger transport provider.

Brake, Mulley, and Nelson (2006) characterised the development of DRT systems and suggest that such systems should develop and/or have developed towards open-access services with flexible times and routes, as is illustrated in Figure 1.

Considering the operator type of most DRTs, it is straightforward that DRTs are seen as derivatives of public transport systems, adjusted to demand-based services where someone can decide more specifically when to go where. However, this characterization is regarded from a rather functional viewpoint, since the focus is mainly on organizational aspects of the service to increase passenger numbers. For example, Brake et al. (2007) suggest that centralizing bookings and the implementation of ICT systems for GPS tracking are necessary, because that is how a high occupancy ratio will be obtained. Contradictorily enough, this focus shifts away from the user perspective.

In our field-research on mobility-based product-service systems, we found that the service of the traditional systems leaves room for improvement. To address social challenges, we propose it is not always necessary to make a service work more efficiently, but rather to improve the service experience of the people involved. Our preliminary findings suggest that a DRT that is set up as a social innovation and that involves multiple stakeholder groups in a rural area can be a better alternative for the user.

DRTs in the Netherlands: the Dutch situation

Sloman and Hendy (2008) saw Dutch DRT services as good examples of how a DRT service should be. RegioTaxi, for example, is a common and rather flexible DRT service. It could be booked in advance, has no fixed route, and no special stops. It is however possible that other passengers will be picked up during a journey. The service could be offered to indicated people, such as seniors and the impaired, and is then called WMO transport, which is a subsidized collective transport. Nelson et al. (2010) described the Dutch Regio-Taxi in the Arnhem-Nijmegen area as a very popular service, which is 'a combination of community transport, STS (Special Transport Services) and open shared-ride taxi services for non-eligible users'. They found that one third of the users travelled subsidized.

RegioTaxi had grown towards a countrywide network, defined by rules and regulations. We conducted a short study to the rules and regulations of highly responsive services such as RegioTaxi and, although it was intended for improving social connectedness, we learned that interpersonal aspects were very strictly defined. Although these services provide transportation to indicated people, the services are still run by large taxi companies and the service provision is defined by rules and regulations, that suggest resemblances with public transport services. Therefore, it is questionable whether DRTs are truly suitable to solve the needs of its users.

The service could offer two types of service. The first type is departure-oriented with priority on an arrival time within thirty minutes before and after the booked departure time. The other type is arrival-oriented for trips that have an arrival priority, for example an appointment in the hospital. These

trips guaranteed that the client will arrive on time, but this could be half an hour early.

Regardless of the trip type, the client must be in the vehicle in less than two minutes after the arrival of the taxi, otherwise the driver is allowed to leave without the client. The driver must be recognizable as a driver. A client is not allowed to take more than one piece of hand luggage, unless it was mentioned during the reservation. Moreover, travelling with a pet is usually not allowed. Eating and drinking is prohibited and cameras could be installed to safeguard the passenger security ('Vervoerreglement Regiotaxi Gelderland', 2013; 'Vervoerreglement Regiotaxi Twente', 2009).

The success of RegioTaxi was discussed by Harms (2008). RegioTaxi is an open-access service, but he found, in contrast to Nelson et al. (2010) that the large amount of trips is WMO transport-based. As a consequence, he argued that the ability to offer satisfying mobility for seniors in rural areas, who are not impaired and therefore have no access to subsidized transport, is very limited. Therefore, Harms concluded that RegioTaxi was not able to challenge loneliness among the regular rural elderly.

We find it worrying that DRT services are intended for the transport of people, and that the driver and passenger appear to have an hierarchical driver-passenger relationship. In this case, the driver is recognisable as a driver and his task is to offer service, but at the same time he has to run the service within predefined time scales. DRTs might be developed to aim at countering social challenges, such as loneliness, but the viewpoint of most organizations seems to be more on the organizational aspect of running a profitable business and increasing passenger numbers, rather than a social viewpoint of understanding what role mobility can play in people's lives. Many restrictions seem to have the intention to control passenger numbers, improve time efficiency and to make the service a well-oiled machine that transports as many passengers as possible with as little hassle as possible. This development is also addressed by Sloman and Hendy (2008), who underline that the function of DRTs is not only economical, but also social; for instance, in order to prevent loneliness.

Summarized, it appears that the flexibility of many DRTs is restricted with an increasing number of customers, and the service provision does not seem to relate to a deeper understanding of people. The functional and calculative way of solving problems does not result in the ideal form of transport, either for subsidized users nor regular users. We doubt, however, whether it is *transportation* that people need. We consider mobility not to be about the act of transportation, but as a tool that supports achieving goals, such as satisfying daily activities.

SKEWIEL MOBIEL: A SOCIAL ALTERNATIVE

If a DRT is a social innovation, social challenges would be the main driver for DRT existence. Therefore, emphasis on the people involved with the service and a good understanding

of what demand means, is necessary for a DRT to be a social innovation.

In this paper we will elaborate on a test bed that we have been studying for several years: Skewiel Mobiel. Addressing social challenges drives Skewiel Mobiel, which is a highly flexible DRT with a high social impact. The service fits with catalytic innovations, i.e. due to the character of the service provider, and because the service has started with a spartan electric vehicle, which managed to bring people where they wanted to go, it was thereby able to suit a social demand. The test bed has been monitored for over four years, both quantitatively, e.g., in terms of how many times the service was used and what locations are visited, and qualitatively, by interviewing users of the service and drivers. This offered us a deep insight into the working principles of the service, of how multiple stakeholders experience the service, and how the service impacted on the local society. With Skewiel Mobiel, the care provider aims at social aspects such as preventing loneliness and stimulating social connectedness on a very small scale within a socially coherent network. Skewiel Mobiel is based on the same social principles as DRT services, but it manages to address these principles more effectively, as will be further elaborated in this study.

QUANTITATIVE STUDY OF SKEWIEL MOBIEL

The service area

Skewiel Mobiel runs in a rural area in the northern part of The Netherlands, named Tytsjerksteradiel. See Table 1 for a compact characterization. It is serviced with one small, three-seated electric vehicle (see Figure 2), and the former electric four-seater as a back-up vehicle (see Figure 3). Volunteer drivers drive the vehicles from the same area as the passengers. In that area, facilities for daily life can be found, such as shops, supermarkets, a library, and medical facilities. Many senior dwellers have been living in this area their whole life and they do not intend to leave the area for a care home in the city, which is in line with the national trend (Kullberg, 2002).

TYTSJERKSTRADIEL
20 x 25 kilometers
32000 inhabitants
17 villages (biggest: +/-10000 inhabitants, smallest: +/- 200 inhabitants)

Table 1: Characterization of Tytsjerksteradiel
Source: Gemeente Tytsjerkstradiel (2014)

Figure 2: Skewiel Mobilie

Figure 3: Back-up vehicle for the Skewiel Mobilie service

Quantitative data

The trip data for the quantitative study was derived from booking information managed by the care provider's reception. The dataset consists of data from the period of 1st November 2012, until 20th December 2013. A total of 482 trips have been registered by a total of 67 unique users.

Most trips were return trips, which usually means that the driver waits or joins the activity until the activity is finished. Some trips were single directional, and eight trips were registered to contain more destinations. For 120 trips, the trip type has not been registered.

Destinations and destination type

The service area of Skewiel Mobilie is rather small. It spans an area of roughly 20 x 25 km. Figure 4 represents the villages in the area and the most important infrastructure. We have chosen to create visual representations of the data, as it provides insight into the high amount of short distance trips made by the service. Moreover, it can be seen that the larger amount of trips were made within or around one village in

Figure 4: Quantitative representation of Skewiel Mobilie destinations. Circles represent various villages that have been serviced by Skewiel Mobilie and their respective distances, i.e. 'OEN' represents Oenkerk, 'GYT' represents Gytsjerk. Arrow thickness represents the relative trip frequency.

the area: Oenkerk (labelled 'OEN'). Oenkerk is the stand for Skewiel Mobilie, the care provider is located in Oenkerk, and many clients live close to the care provider. Frequently visited villages (i.e. Gytsjerk: 'GYT' or Aldtsjerk: 'ALD') were found within a range of three kilometres around Oenkerk.

The maximum travelled trip distance during the monitoring period is approximately fifteen kilometres, which has been registered only two times. About two thirds of all trips are made within a distance of three km, which is a common cycling distance in The Netherlands. One third of all trips were inside a village and many people could perfectly walk these distances. However, the wide distribution of users consisted of people who have difficulties with walking and could not ride their bike or car anymore. In addition, the people who were able to walk within their home village used Skewiel Mobilie for the slightly longer distances to the neighbouring village.

Figure 5 shows that roughly half of all trips are shopping related. This can be either a visit to the supermarket, or to other shops. During the monitoring period, we learned that many trips consisted of more than one stop, although this was not mentioned in the booking diary. So, for example, a client can first visit the supermarket and thereafter the bakery or the butcher next door.

Next to shopping and visiting the supermarket, many clients use Skewiel Mobil for visiting medical facilities such as the family doctor, dentist or pharmacy, or visiting the care centre for facilities, such as the restaurant, physical therapy, or for organized social activities.

Interestingly, socially oriented trips (visiting friends or family) are not often undertaken using Skewiel Mobil. Skewiel Mobil seems to be used generally for trips to maintain everyday life. Because the service area of Skewiel Mobil offers many facilities in and around the village, this results in very short distances that are uncommon to public transport and other DRT services. The trip data showed that 62% of the trips took an hour or less.

Qualitative user interviews

User characterization

For the qualitative analysis, we conducted non-structured interviews with drivers, and semi-structured interviews with eight frequent users of Skewiel Mobil. During the interviews, the interviewer and respondents were free to elaborate on pre-defined questions and answers. The respondents' use frequency varied from monthly to weekly. The focus of all interviews was on the experience of the service.

The people that were interviewed were considered to be typical Skewiel Mobil users. Seven of eight respondents were female; seven of eight lived alone, but independently. Seven of eight were using a wheeled walker, and what seems to characterize all people is their lack of access to a car.

Booking process

Users mentioned that they highly appreciated the service of Skewiel Mobil during the booking process. The booking process was generally regarded as very easy and respondents appreciated the fact that a trip could be booked at the last moment.

The receptionist knows most users by name and knows the area. In addition, he is familiar with most clients and their frequent trips. Booking goes in a two-way direction. The client proposes a time and the receptionist and client discuss whether that is suitable. If someone else has already booked the service, both parties agree on another time. The receptionist or client estimate how long a trip will take and the booking is made.

Reasons for use

Users of Skewiel Mobil generally have limited access to other types of transportation. Most respondents were not able to ride a bike anymore and all use a walker outside, although two also have to use a walker indoors. One respondent mentioned not being able to leave her house at all, but most users have difficulties with walking longer distances, and use Skewiel Mobil to overcome the distance to the shop. As we also found out from the trip data, such short trips are amongst the typical trips that are made with Skewiel Mobil. A second reason that was mentioned for the use of Skewiel Mobil was the waiting time for the closest alternative: WMO transport. Respondents were not satisfied with the time interval in which this taxi service arrives. They appreciated that Skewiel Mobil arrives on the agreed time, that drivers are familiar, and that drivers wait or help during an activity. One respondent did not see any advantages over mobility alternatives, but he agreed that the service is useful for others for a quick shopping run.

The above shows that users have a general appreciation for specific characteristics of Skewiel Mobil, such as the short distances that are possible and the high reliability. Respondents were also directly asked what they appreciated about the service. Most respondents pointed out that they liked the idea of having a mobility option closely available when they need it, even if they do not need it continuously. Hence, being a back-up option can be considered a very high social value of the service.

Impact on everyday life

Respondents were also asked how they expect to be affected if Skewiel Mobil disappeared. This question was asked to estimate the perceived impact of the service on everyday life. In general, respondents mentioned that they would use

Figure 5: Destination types of Skewiel Mobil. Arrow thickness represents the relative trip number. i.e. Most trips headed to destination 'supermarket', 'shopping', or 'unknown'

alternatives, such as WMO taxi, or that they would reduce their outgoing trips. Delivery services were also proposed, for example for groceries or library books, but two respondents mentioned that the drawback was that they would like to see a product before buying or borrowing it.

These answers were in line with how most users use Skewiel Mobiel for daily activities. Using it certainly has an impact on their daily lives, because unavailability of this service would mean a reduction of the amount of daily activities. This suggests that Skewiel Mobiel provides a service that satisfies needs which are not provided by regular services.

Social impact for drivers

We have elaborated on the social impact for clients, but clients are not the only users of this service. The drivers, especially, are important stakeholders in the Skewiel Mobiel service, as they also benefit from the social impact. All drivers are volunteers, and they live in the same area as the clients. Most drivers are retired, but some of the drivers are unemployed for a different reason. Most drivers mentioned that they were looking for a day activity and they see Skewiel Mobiel as an ideal opportunity to be of use.

The relationship between drivers and clients is generally very good. Oftentimes, the driver accompanies the passenger during activities and acts more as a buddy, rather than as a servant. With the help of the driver, passengers are able to perform activities they cannot do alone. This is an underestimated advantage of this service; it increases social connectedness, and more classical DRT systems would not have made this possible. Skewiel Mobiel is therefore not a door-to-door service, but a door-through-door service.

The social value of Skewiel Mobiel for the drivers became clear when they mentioned being unsatisfied with the frequency of the trips. Sometimes, a low number of trips per day were booked and the drivers did not like this at all. Therefore, the service provider tried to increase the trip frequency, but from a social perspective and not from an economical perspective. As a result, the care provider made an agreement with a local mental healthcare provider to offer contracted trips between housing and activity centres.

CONCLUSION

DRTs might be considered as social innovation, because they aim at solving social challenges and primarily serve forgotten parts of society.

However, we argued that DRTs are not set-up as a social innovation. A DRT that is designed as a social innovation will be based on different principles that are less organizational and more user-centred. Therefore, its structure will look different from that of traditional DRTs.

We found that Skewiel Mobiel is a very good example of a social innovation, partly because the service was set-up by a

care provider that is very well acquainted with the seniors in the area. As a result, it is not bound to a mobility business structure or biased by what a mobility service should look like, and it addresses challenges in its own way. The care provider had a good idea of what seniors needed to increase their independency and social connectedness and Skewiel Mobiel can be considered a success, not because of how well it is organized, but because of how well it connects with people's daily lives. Two thirds of the trips are made within a range of a few kilometres of which half of the trips are even made within a range of a few 100 metres, and this is a range that is unfamiliar for traditional DRT systems.

Destinations that Skewiel Mobiel users visit are usually for simple activities to maintain everyday life. The functional goal of such situations, such as having fresh food in house, or having a new haircut, can be satisfied by delivery services and home services. Therefore, the functional incentive to leave the house is not apparent, but leaving the house is very important for independence, social connectedness, and the well-being of all people, including seniors. We found that Skewiel Mobiel stands out from other mobility services, because it provides the freedom to leave the house and lets people live life in an ordinary way. Hereby, Skewiel Mobiel reveals itself as a social and catalytic innovation, since the service explicitly focuses on the social good and serves the underestimated need of its users to continue simple, daily life activities; something that is very common for 'ordinary' people, but seemingly uncommon for seniors that suffer reduced mobility. Hence, the social impact of Skewiel Mobiel seems to be especially defined by the ability to limit the social impact of decreasing mobility. In other words: Skewiel Mobiel seems to be fairly well accepted, because people are motivated to continue the life they are used to. It fits very well to habits that people used to have.

On top of that, the social impact of the service does not only affect passengers. The service has an impact on the larger social network, such as the volunteer drivers. They like to be of use for others and they enjoy their role in Skewiel Mobiel. Their loyalty, shown by their dissatisfaction with a low trip frequency and a high motivation to help, shows that they appreciate how Skewiel Mobiel works as a platform that also impacts their lives.

DISCUSSION

From our continuous monitoring of the Skewiel Mobiel service, we found that planning an activity is not a problem for a lot of seniors. However, insecurity about when the activity starts seems to be very frustrating. Moreover, we found that they do not like to devote a few hours of the day to something that used to take less than an hour, just because their mobility has been reduced.

Nevertheless, deteriorating mobility is inevitable, as growing older comes with decreasing abilities, both cognitive and physical. The valuable back-up character of Skewiel Mobiel

became clear as the respondents mentioned that they plan to use Skewiel Mobiel more often if their mobility situation becomes worse. This suggests that lots of seniors do not necessarily fear deterioration itself, but the results of deterioration. So, although they have to give in on the reality of deterioration, it is straightforward that they prepare for the next alternative. In this context, the existence of services like Skewiel Mobiel, but also other DRT alternatives is crucial for seniors. However, what makes Skewiel Mobiel stand out is its flexibility and reliability, which allows the normal act of events to take around the same time as it normally does. Moreover, the company of a driver as a buddy transforms such trips into a social event. Therefore the social impact of deterioration stays limited.

For a designer, it is essential to have a thorough understanding of the social problem to design for, and familiarity with the users can let an organization be innovative in a field that they are unfamiliar with. Design of a service will then look totally different from the services they are used to designing, developing and exploiting. Moreover, we think that design does not always have to change people's lives. Sometimes it may be better to help people retain what they are used to doing, but find it difficult to achieve now. Losing everyday life patterns, or habits, can be painful and we think Skewiel Mobiel is a success because it enables its users to retain the life that they were used to.

It has shown to be rewarding to focus on the simple activities that are sometimes closer to the surface than they appear; this can be done by using simple, but very useful, tools. Skewiel Mobiel is a simple service for simple activities, but it has a high impact because it addresses everyday life patterns. Skewiel Mobiel shows that it is not necessary to optimize numbers, to use measurable performance indicators, and to define rules and regulations to run a service as fluid as possible. Of course, there are restrictions, but the case of Skewiel Mobiel shows that design from within a social network, established for this social network, supported by a thorough understanding of people's daily lives, and intended to maintain, can result in a very successful service that plays an important role for the entire community.

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IN THE MAKING: MATERIAL AND IMMATERIAL TRANSFORMATIONS IN COLOMBIAN INDIGENOUS COMMUNITIES

Emilia Atuesta Pradilla
✉ emiliaatuesta@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This paper explores the analytical status of “hybrid” material transformations that flourish in the indigenous communities of Vichada, Colombia, building on previous relevant work in the area of creativity and value perception. It suggests that the approach to materiality as “becoming” rather than “being” reveals a strategy of creation and recreation of value and identity through the production of meaningful connections in a changing environment. This creation of value is achieved through action, and more specifically by means of the act of making, revealing a selective and active approach towards the material world.

KEYWORDS: *material culture, creativity, appropriation, transformation, making*

INTRODUCTION

Material culture crafted by indigenous people in Vichada, Colombia is being continually modified in response to the changing environment. Women squeeze bitter cassava turning it into artefacts made of natural fibres or packaging tape; kids run around the communities playing with cars made from motor oil bottles; plastic chairs are sown together to keep them from falling apart; and a caiman skin merges with a metal structure to become a chair. These transformations challenge the understanding of tradition and continuity and value creativity and the production of meaningful connections.

This paper will focus on a series of objects, interventions, modifications and translations that flourish in indigenous communities in Vichada. These materializations are made up not only of natural resources, but also of industrial materials that have become accessible to the communities as a result of urban expansion. ‘New’ materials acquire meaning in their interaction with people, and specifically through the act of making and using, becoming part of their daily communal lives. It is a process of appropriation (Schneider, 2006), whereby materials are selectively incorporated and transformed acquiring value in the new compositions.

Making, as a traditional way of satisfying needs, constitutes not only a specific approach to the environment and a physical and symbolic practice, but also results in a materialization that presents itself as a frozen image of relations. The materiality of making represents a pause in the flow, an

objectification that has the ability to speak in a unique way (Tilley2006:62), which permits the observer, or we may say the listener, to unravel the web behind it. By studying the traces of relations in the process of making, and the use of resources in a changing environment, one can understand how these transformations come into being and how they are valued in their specific context.

LITERATURE REVIEW: CREATIVE TRANSFORMATIONS

This paper will examine the analytical status of material transformations in the everyday communal life of indigenous people in Vichada. Pivotal to this is the body of literature surrounding creativity as an essential element in the processes of transformation of the material world. Additionally, it is important to take into account the discussions around the relationship between people and things and to explore the literature on hybridity as a way of understanding what things (and people) are made of.

Engaging with things from the perspective of making brings questions that go beyond materiality to discover their more intricate conformation, both material and immaterial. Ingold (2007, 2012) advocates for the dematerialization of materiality, looking to move toward an *ecology of materials* where the attention focuses on the flows of materials that give rise to the things themselves. Similarly, Holbraad (2011) proposes a prag-

matological model that values material properties as generators of conceptual affordances that can set the terms for the understanding of things.

These perspectives move away from the ontological distinction between subjects and objects, which places the human as the centre of the system of relations. Within this ontology, Miller's (2005) approach is based on the dialectical process of objectification, where things, through their interaction with people, contribute to the definition of the latter. However, in this specific relationship, things can be said to be already made physically and only in the making symbolically. As Appadurai (1986) affirms, things have a social life and they are modified as they move and interact with people; however, what is considered malleable is their meaning more than their material composition. The status of things then, has been discussed both in terms of their wholeness and of their configuration resulting in different levels of understanding of their interaction. By looking at objects in the making, but moving forward to understand their further relation to the users, who, in this case, are commonly the same makers, one can begin to unravel the multiple significances of things and make connections between these levels.

The material and immaterial transformation of things is the result of a creative process; therefore, creativity can be considered an important concept to analyse as a strategy of engagement with things and materials. To understand this concept, Leach (2004) explains that there is not just one creativity, but modes of creativity that are shaped by different contexts. Appropriative creativity is the materialization of an intellectual input, which aims for an economic profit, while distributive creativity goes beyond the tangible result to value the making of connections (see Levi-Strauss, 1966). Ingold and Hallam (2007) explain the concept in terms of the on-going process of life. It is not just the specific instantiation of novel creation (see Liep, 2001), but a process of adaptation that not only produces things, but also transforms the people involved. Creativity then, is a concept that links people and things, and can allow us to explore the connections between the elements that make up their interaction.

By decomposing the whole into its constituent parts and the way that they are attached to each other through the creative process, one begins to understand both people and things in a different way. The relational make-up of events reveals an inherent hybridity behind every complete form (García Canciani, 1997; Amselle, 1998; Baron, 2011; Clifford, 2002; Schneider, 2006). To go beyond the search for pure original forms, Amselle (1998) proposes to think in terms of an originary syncretism, which results from a constant practice of negotiation of identity. This process is conceptualized by Schneider (2006) in terms of appropriation. According to him, appropriation is a strategy for identity construction whereby a subject uses an external element and invests it with meaning in a new composition; altering both the element and himself. It is a dynamic process where all of the elements involved are active in their mutual constitution, and so, their existence depends on this encounter.

RESEARCH

The data presented in this paper was collected during two years' of fieldwork in indigenous communities in Vichada, Colombia, while working with the NGO *Fundación Etnollano*.² I joined the sustainable production team as a design advisor, working with groups of indigenous artisans and helping them develop sustainable craft processes based on their traditional knowledge. During this time, I studied the way that the communities relate to their material culture, gaining an understanding of their approach to making and resources. Even though my work was related to traditional crafts, I began to observe the way that other more "hybrid" creations were made and used within the communities and began to study these covert creations.

The research was undertaken mainly through participant observation and informal conversations. I conducted interviews with 5 artisans from 3 communities with different ethnic backgrounds (*Piaroa*, *Sikuani* and *Amorúa*), regarding the alternative transformations in opposition to what they call traditional crafts. I used photo elicitation, with images of a collection of objects from the three communities (*Cachicamo*, *Joval* and *Guáripa*) in order to talk about the stories of how they came to be and the role that they play within the communities.

This paper unravels the stories, meanings and connections that develop around 4 hybrid objects, which represent many other instances present within the communities. These examples were selected not only because of the willingness of the creators and users to discuss their existence, but also because of the objects' capacity to represent important characteristics that can be extrapolated to other cases of hybrid transformation.

Case 1: Material Affordances: The Plastic Sebucán

The *sebucán* is one of the most important elements to prepare *bitter cassava*.³ It is used for squeezing the poison out of the root, to make it edible. It has a specific weaving pattern that

1 2010-2012

2 The NGO, *Fundación Etnollano*, has been linked to these lands since it was founded in 1985, working towards the improvement of the quality of life of indigenous, rural and marginal communities. To achieve this aim, they work on projects related to health, environmental and ethno-education, protection of cultural heritage and sustainable production. For further information see www.etnollano.org

3 Bitter cassava is one of the basic plants cultivated by the indigenous people of Vichada. This root is highly nutritious and hence, an important part of their daily diet. There is a rich material culture around bitter cassava, which responds to a particular way of cultivation, preparation and cooking. The preparation of this plant for consumption is very important because the root itself, without the proper process, is poisonous to both human beings and animals.

Figure 1. *Sebucán* made of plastic packaging tape and *tirita* in the community of *Cachicamo*. Image taken by the author.

tightens its contents as it is pulled in order to extract all of the liquid from the grated cassava⁴.

In the community of *Cachicamo*⁵, the traditional *sebucán* made from *tirita*, a natural fibre, is hanging next to one made from green plastic packaging tape. This object maintains its traditional shape and use but has undergone a material translation. Even though the plastic *sebucán* works well and lasts longer than the other, it does not necessarily replace the original object, which provides a tighter squeeze.

Packaging tape from the remains of the packages of different products transported from the cities is a material that is often found in urban centres. It is considered trash within the urban context; however, as Strassler (1999) affirms, “What counts as trash has always depended on who is counting” (p.289). Thompson (1979) explains that the way that we act towards an object depends on a categorization, which is necessarily social. According to him, objects are divided into three categories: durable, transient and rubbish. The first two make up the overt or visible part of the system and they differ in terms of their lifespan and value. The durable category is characterized by the ability to acquire value in time and has an (ideally) infinite lifespan, while the objects within the transient category lose value in time and have a finite lifespan (Ibid). Rubbish, on the other hand, conforms the covert or invisible part of the system being value-less. This third category becomes important for the dynamics of the whole system because it is located in a region of flexibility that is not subject to the same control mechanisms. Hence, it is possible for rubbish to be transferred into one of the overt categories, arising as a potentially temporary and mutable category that can ac-

quire value and be re-categorized through an act of discovery (Ibid).

The packaging tape falls into the transient category whilst in use in the urban context, as soon as the package is unpacked, the tape enters the rubbish category completely losing its value. However, once it is recognized by the indigenous people and used to weave a *sebucán*, it re-enters the transient category starting a new lifespan.

The plastic *sebucán* represents a transfer between categories, changing the way that people act around this specific material. In the eyes of the indigenous people of *Cachicamo*, packaging tape is never rubbish, for they recognize its characteristics and appreciate the material in relation to what it can become. This sensitivity in terms of materials and their properties promotes a diminishment of the rubbish category and reveals a cyclical view of things fostered by continual transformations.

These transformations are triggered by the affordances of things. The term affordance, coined by Gibson (1986), refers to what the material, in this case, has to offer to the person that engages with it (Ibid p.127). Knappet (2004) explains the concept in terms of relationality, whereby the affordances come not from the object or from the person, but from the situation of encounter (Ibid p. 46).

If one considers the packaging tape and its dissimilar categorization in the urban and indigenous contexts, one can begin to understand how the perception of affordances promotes action, and through action, value is created or destroyed. The packaging tape, by having similar characteristics to the natural fibre used to make a *sebucán*, affords weaving to those sensitive to material properties, triggering a creative process that ends up changing its categorization and entering the realm of elements available for transformation.

Case 2: Making Connections: The *Makibü* Chair

There is a remarkable diversity of chairs in the community of *Joval*⁶, which have all been transformed and adapted. The *Makibü* chair is a particularly interesting example; it stands out for being aesthetically different although it is considered to be a chair like any other. It does not have a particular owner, it does not signify a hierarchical position, as Elvira⁷ explains, “I have it there and everyone sits on it.” Listening to the story of how it came to be, one realizes that it is just one option out of many, the result of a successful trial in the

4 Men normally make this artefact; it is one of the craft activities that any man must master in order to be able to marry. He must provide her with the necessary baskets for their day-to-day life and she, on the other hand, is in charge of preparing the food using these artefacts.

5 The community of *Cachicamo* is a *Piaroa* community located in the *Resguardo Cachicamo* in the lower Orinoco River, near the city of Puerto Ayacucho in Venezuela.

6 The community of *Joval* is located in the *Resguardo la Hormiga*, north of *Cachicamo* and closer to the urban centre of Puerto Carreño in Colombia

7 Elvira is the oldest woman of the community, and mother and grandmother to many of the community members and leader of the group of artisans of *Joval*.

8 Elvira explains that there are many *Makibü* in the nearby rivers, but the men do not kill them everyday. “They are forbidden animals”, she says, not traditionally but by the local authorities that believe they must be protected. For this reason, the indigenous men hunt them once in a while and use them for communal consumption only.

FIGURE 2: Makibü chair in the community of Joval Image taken by the author

creative flow that has survived because of its efficiency within the specific context.

Makibü is the Sikuani word for a type of caiman that lives in the nearby rivers which is killed and eaten by the people.⁸ The story of the chair is quite simple; the men went out fishing and caught a *Makibü*, they took the meat and left the skin to rot. But one of the fishermen saw the skin laying there and had an idea; he was not looking for a way to use the skin, he did not particularly need a chair, he just remembered the existence of the metal structure and realized that the shape of these two different materialities could fit together in an interesting way. He decided to take the skin with him to the community and give his idea a try. It worked, and so, they began using this newly created chair. It was a good chair; made from available resources and comfortable. Seeing that there were several metal structures lying around the community⁹, the fisherman decided that he could make another chair. So the next time that he caught a *Makibü*, he carefully took the skin off and let it dry. However Elvira remembers that one of the dogs took the skin and destroyed it, so he gave up on his idea.

The *Makibü* chair materializes a connection between natural resources and industrial materials. The fisherman acts as a bricoleur, who uses different elements found within his environment and relates them in a specific way (Lévi-Strauss, 1966). As Lévi-Strauss explains, “The decision as to what to put in each place also depends on the possibility of putting a different element there instead, so that each choice which is made will involve a complete reorganization of the structure, which will never be the same as one vaguely imag-

9 Probably remains from chairs received as donations or from the nearby school or even bought by one of the community members in Puerto Carreño.

ined nor as some other which might have been preferred to it” (Lévi-Strauss, 1966 p.19). The metal structure could have been connected to different materials to make a chair (or even a different end), but the fisherman’s decision, in his relation to both the affordances of the materials and his environment, resulted in one possibility.

This materialization represents a relational potential that is realized in the world as an outcome of the creative flow. The interchangeability of elements depicted by Lévi-Strauss in his description of bricolage generates material structures that have weaker physical bonds between their components. This, in turn, ends up promoting the understanding of objects, not as fixed materialities, but as constructions, valuing the parts as much as the whole, and allowing these to become instruments for further action (Leach, 2004).

Following this conceptualization, the indigenous people’s approach to the environment and their daily practice is part of a creative flow that engenders their living conditions and allows them to move through time in a constant regeneration. Creativity appears as a way to cope with the encounter, promoting an inclusive approach towards the changing conditions of the environment. The appreciation of materials as “becoming” rather than “being”, and the inclusion of the new resources within their milieu as part of their field of action, allows them to interact within this particular context.

This understanding of the material world overturns the hylomorphic model of creation¹⁰ criticized by Ingold (2010) whereby the people impose form on materials, and opens up into an inverted approach. From this perspective and in relation to making, creativity is not about the objects that it is able to produce, but about the way that the maker and the materials interact and are modified by the act of making. This shifts the perspective from the result to the process of making, allowing to trace the transformations rather than to search for material and cultural stability (Ibid). The chair is a temporal object, which is able to fulfil a function as a whole; however, it will always be a composition that cannot only be taken apart, but also be made again in the same and many different ways.

Case 3: Revaluing Elements: The Toy Car

The boys from the Guáripa¹¹ community play with a very interesting toy: an empty motor oil bottle made into a car. With the intro-

10 “To create any thing, Aristotle reasoned, you have to bring together form (morphe) and matter (hyle). In the subsequent history of Western thought, this hylomorphic model of creation became ever more deeply embedded. But it also became increasingly unbalanced. Form came to be seen as imposed by an agent with a particular design in mind, while matter, thus rendered passive and inert, became that which was imposed upon.” (Ingold, 2010, p.92)

11 The community of Guáripa is located in the Resguardo Caño Guáripa, only a thirty-minute boat ride from the urban centre of Puerto Carreño. The Amorúa people were traditionally nomads; moving from one place to another has led them to become masters of adaptation.

duction of engines to the community, these bottles have become part of their environment, available resources waiting to be used.

In general, all of the components of this unique toy speak about the community and its relations, about the changes in their environment. The shape of the bottle resembles that of a car, which the children have seen either in the nearby urban centres or even just on television. The wheels are plastic bottle caps, of different shapes and sizes, collected either from visitors, home groceries, or in the urban centres. They are attached to the bottle with lollipop sticks, which are the remains of gifts commonly brought by visitors to the children of *Guáripa*. The car is thus an ensemble of different plastic disposable elements that only acquire value through action, when combined to create a coherent form.

The making process comes about through collaboration between the children and their fathers. The kids collect the different elements around the community and the men put the toys together. The territory where this car must travel is rocky, bumpy and steep, so the children have adapted a string, from their mothers' weaving fibres and tied it to a stick to be able to, tied to a stick, to be able to pull the car. As a result of their experience with the car in movement, they have decided to place stones inside it, giving it the necessary weight to prevent it from turning over.

This toy relates internal objects and concepts with external objects and concepts resulting in an objectification of a hybrid reality. It goes beyond the idea of an individual maker, to uncover the way in which community members, through their family relations, are involved together in the creation of material culture. The toy car, as an ensemble, is the result of a series of characteristics and events that are part of the lives of the indigenous people: the act of moving on motorboats, groceries brought from the urban centres, sweets given by visitors to the children, women weaving string bags, kids climbing on trees to get sticks, a community constructed on the rocks.

The use of elements considered as trash to make new compositions that serve a different purpose, has been categorized

as *recyclia* or third-world recycling (Dziedzic, 2008). This understanding of the objects focuses on the elements and their previous uses, making their new appreciation interesting for those who are familiar with the use and discarded of their components (Kratz, 1995). Kratz (1995) criticizes this approach, proposing to rethink the transformations from the maker's perspective instead of just admiring the irony of their existence. She affirms that people celebrate *recyclia's* productivity and creativity, but few have analysed the conditions where these transformations arise (Ibid). Therefore, instead of grouping these objects in one external category, they can be used as a starting-point to analyse the culture where and for which they are produced (Coote, 2000).

At first sight, the existence of these objects in the community of *Guáripa*, signals what Cerny (1996) describes as the "ubiquitous intrusion of material modernity in even the remotest corners of the world" (Ibid p.12). However, when one realizes that this material modernity is selectively incorporated and transformed by the people of the community, intrusion does not seem like the appropriate term to characterize the interaction. It is a process of appropriation that transforms each of the elements giving them meaning in relation to the new composition. Seen in this light, the indigenous people of *Guáripa* are not passive observers of the 'intrusion' of modernity, but are engaged in an active transformation of their material environment.

This process of appropriation allows the transfer from rubbish to transient, through giving the materialities the possibility of becoming something else. As with the packaging tape and the metal structure, as soon as they acquire meaning within their specific context, the elements are re-categorized, modifying the actions that take place around them. Plastic motor oil bottles cease to be just containers that hold the oil necessary for the movement of the people outside of the community, they become potential toy cars that can promote the movement of the children within the community. Lollipop sticks afford the holding of candy as well as that of wheels, and plastic bottle caps are valued for their ability to roll on the rocks.

FIGURE 3: Motor oil bottle car in the community of *Guáripa* Image taken by the author

FIGURE 4: Reconstructed chair in the community of *Joval* Image taken by the author

Case 4: Artefacts of Attachment: The Reconstructed Chair

In the community of *Joval*, a chair that has been completely and proudly sewn up shows the scars that evidence its story. This reconstructed chair reveals an amazingly different understanding of materials and their characteristics; the broken plastic has been ingeniously sewn together with nylon thread, giving the object a new life. It integrates fishing materials, plastic and traditional sewing techniques in a very unexpected way.

As Strassler (1999) affirms, “repair ideas come more easily to people who make things” (p.10). Their tactile understanding of objects goes beyond wholeness, to the properties of materials and their possibilities of transformation. Therefore, a broken object does not necessarily lose its value, but it becomes available for revaluation through the creative process. Objects made and used by the indigenous people in their daily lives are normally repaired to extend their lifespan. This mending process is different from other processes of transformation in that it prolongs the life of the object and so its specific purpose, instead of the life of the materials, beyond their configuration as objects. In other words, certain objects resist being transformed into something different, maintaining their integrity as objects for a longer time.

The story of this chair reveals a mending process, stimulated not by its functionality, but by the emotional significance tied to the object. The original plastic blue chair had been brought to the community from Puerto Carreño as a present to one of the men. His uncle, who lived in the urban centre, had earned enough money to buy a gift for him. He proudly brought the chair to the community; a plastic chair which would last longer than others, a chair that could get wet, be easily cleaned and resist exposure to outside conditions. Although this chair belonged to one specific man, it soon became used by all of the community members, like most of the objects present in *Joval*, which tend to move around from person to person. Some months later, the uncle died in an accident; this event modified the value of the chair completely. It changed from being just a chair to becoming the memory of a lost loved one; it acquired an emotional importance in the eyes of the nephew; a physical connection to an immaterial relation. But, the physical does not last as long as the emotional. The durability of plastic is threatened by long exposure to the sun, which crystalizes the material making it brittle.

Elvira remembers that the children broke the chair into many pieces, while playing with it on a sunny day. The nephew could not stand the idea of having his uncle’s chair shattered into pieces, so he began to sew. He took all of the pieces and put them together like a puzzle. He began by making holes with a warm nail on the edges of the broken plastic. He used the nails left from the construction of houses and the fire from the communal kitchen. He then decided to put it all together by using a nylon thread, a material used for fishing that proved to be more resistant than organic fibres. He spent a long time sewing the pieces together using the traditional cross pattern to make it stronger. “He was very patient,” recounts Elvira.

The time invested undertaking such a task, which clearly does not have a functional aim, shows a different appreciation of the creative process. As Sennett states, “The slowness of craft time serves as a source of satisfaction; practice beds in, making the skill one’s own” (Sennett, 2008 p.295). The craft process therefore acquires value in itself through the effect that it has on the people involved.

The transformation of things not only responds to a material curiosity that allows for the practical use of their physical properties in a particular way, but also to the immaterial meanings attached to the physical world. The malleability of materiality is contextually defined, and so, as Ingold (2000) states “The temporal rhythms of life are gradually built into the structural properties of things” (p.345). What seemed like an external object representative of the modern world, was transformed through interaction into a highly personalized metaphorical medium. The plastic chair, through its process of transformation (both of breaking and mending), objectifies the experience of a man living in the community of *Joval*.

CONCLUSIONS

The material culture of the indigenous communities of Vichada includes transformations that are the result of the encounter with the urban centres and the “modern” way of life. They evidence the effacement of barriers between these two worlds and a latent creativity that transforms the external into familiar compositions that adapt to a changing context. In this context, the act of making reasserts its position as the traditional way of transforming the properties of materials to favour the people in their daily practice. It is through the physical creation of things that people are able to cope with the encounter, creating and recreating their identity.

The possibility of transformation arises through the encounter between the indigenous people and the material world, and therefore it cannot be attributed to any of the two on their own, but to the more complex result of their moments of interaction. Making things for use composes a system that is entangled prior to any instantiation, strengthening the inherent interdependence. The relationship established between finished elements (subject and object) in the creation of value (Simmel, 1990), degrades into the mutual constitution of potentialities, modifying the pattern of action that takes place between them. From this perspective, value is created in action¹²; it results from the input of energy that transforms affordances into movements. It is the encounter between an indigenous person and a piece of packaging tape that produces a possibility, which leads to the action of weaving. Therefore, value is created not before or after action, but during the physical movement of transformation.

12 Munn’s work describes a similar perspective whereby value emerges in action, yet her conceptualization of value is directly related to the making visible of the human capacity to act through concrete forms (Graeber, 2001 p.45), excluding the essential input of materiality as part of a mutually dependent system.

The understanding of things not as complete objects but partial processes (Ingold, 2012), allows the indigenous people of Vichada to recognize potential in all of the materialities that they encounter while encouraging them to be part of the subsequent transformation towards the creation of a beneficial flow of materials. These processes occur at the level of using, concurring with Miller's (1987) creative consumption and Appadurai's (1986) social life of things. However, they also dig deeper, modifying the most basic physical structures, which in turn change all of the subsequent interactions. If a poisonous root, lethal to human beings and animals, can become the basic food source of the indigenous people of Vichada, anything and everything is possible.

Bitter cassava, like other materialities in this indigenous context, does not depend on its wholeness to be evaluated by the people; if it were so, it would have been discarded as dangerous and eliminated from the possibilities of everyday life. By decomposing it into its most basic parts, the people have found a way to benefit from it, unleashing a process of transformation composed of multiple artefacts, which depend on other transformations in order to exist. It is easy to understand this process from the perspective of men and women transforming their surroundings, yet with a little effort one is also able to picture bitter cassava as the main character, transforming men and women (and their activities) for many generations. This reversed ontology uncovers the impact of materialities and their properties on the people, challenging the supremacy of the subject and depicting a more balanced system of interaction.

Within this system, creativity must necessarily be understood as an on-going process of transformation, which transcends the temporal material instantiations. Therefore, it becomes a concept, which cannot be easily pinned down as the action of a subject on an object, but that involves and demands a confluence of forces in movement. If people make things and things make people (if they can be distinguished in such a way), then neither of them has the required independence to be responsible for the creative act. Creativity does not arise from the person who weaves a plastic *sebacán*, it is the packaging tape discovered in the eyes of the indigenous, which affords the creative transformation, and such an act consequently creates a new *sebacán*; yet also a changed person, and a different packaging tape.¹³

The fisherman making the *Makibū* chair is not searching for a potential solution to a specific problem, he is free from the burden of execution and so, plunges into the domain of uncertainty and risk that encompasses any craft process (Adamson, 2011). What is accomplished then, is not the resulting chair, but the connection established and the possibilities that this connection may bring. As Levi-Strauss (1966) writes in his explanation of the relation between a woodpecker and a toothache, "The real question is not whether the touch of a woodpecker's beak does in fact cure toothache. It is rather whether there is

a point of view from which a woodpecker's beak and a man's tooth can be seen as 'going together'" (Ibid p.9).

In this sense, the *Makibū* skin merges with the metal structure as a feasible possibility, reflecting the potential connection between natural and industrial resources within the indigenous context. The consequent social life of the resulting object in the community endorses the viability of the connection, and in some cases, may result in the reproduction of the same or similar objects. The failed reproduction of the *Makibū* chair due to the intervention of a dog shows the lack of attachment to the material instantiation and the input of different forces in the creative process.

The toy car, on the other hand, exemplifies a successful process of reproduction of connections. The object is reproduced because of the availability of resources, which in the end, signal a reproduction of the social relations that bring these specific resources to the community. Therefore, the persistence of the toy car necessarily implies the movement of men on motorboats and a continual relation with the urban centres. The toy reveals the permeability between the rural and urban worlds on a material and immaterial level, becoming a metaphor for the indigenous reality.

Furthermore, it is an object that evolves with use, going through additional transformations that result from its interaction. The toy car is never finished; it grows with the children and their activities. Therefore it is an object that not only evidences the presence of elements coming from outside the community, but also shows the way that they interact with internal elements, composing a hybrid assembly.

If everything is made up of a combination of elements, what becomes interesting is not only recognizing hybridity, but also being able to decompose things to understand how they come to be and the effect that each one of those elements has through the process of becoming part of the composition. The combination of elements in the making must go through a process of appropriation (Schneider, 2006). It is not only about the materials at hand and how the external elements are digested from the inside in order for them to be able to interact and become part of the creative compositions, but it is also about the way in which the subjects involved in this process suffer their own transformations, re-defining their identities.

The material transformations that flourish in the indigenous communities of Vichada are not only an ingenious way of transforming industrial objects and materials into new compositions with renewed meanings and uses, but a strategy towards the understanding of the other and the construction of their own identity. In Puerto Carreño, a broken plastic chair quickly enters the rubbish category, while in *Joval*, it is transformed into a composition that challenges the passing of time by holding together, through devious means, what was meant to be apart. The reconstruction of the chair not only reveals a unique understanding of materials and their properties, but also the specific significance, attributed to the object through the process of appropriation. Appropriation then, is a modification

13 And one could go further to list the changes that these three modified forces bring about the people around them, their activities, the environment and therefore their culture.

of the physical and semantic structure of materialities, which in turn, modify the system that supports them, including the subject involved in the process. It is through this process that value is created in the indigenous communities of Vichada.

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CRAFT AND FAITH-BASED SOUVENIRS

THE CASE OF TWO CITIES IN TURKEY

Dilek Akbulut

Dr., Gazi University, Faculty of Architecture, Department of Industrial Design

✉ dilekakblt@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Souvenirs are reminders that indicate a particular time, location or attraction and are generally associated with a touristic act or a ceremony. The tourism potential of a province is supported by a souvenir market in which the local identity is commercialized. This paper presents a comparative study of the souvenir market in two touristic locations in Turkey, namely Hacibektas and Konya, particular for their belief tourism. These two destinations are known for their lodges and they attract a considerable number of tourists, both domestic and international. Souvenirs from a sacred place are expected to reflect its sacredness. This secret characteristic is associated with a local underground resource and craft in Hacibektas, while Konya is known as an industrial center as well. The aim of the study is to scrutinize the motives behind small scale faith-based souvenir production, and its relationship with craft.

KEYWORDS: *souvenir, design, faith, craft, belief tourism.*

INTRODUCTION

The recent souvenir market demonstrates conventional patterns of products in nearly every tourist destination. Although souvenirs are expected to reflect the local identity with local production patterns, indigenous sources and local indicators, they can be found far away from where they were produced. Traditional crafts appear to reflect local identity as they depend on native resources. Craft also operates as a means to sanctify a gift. For this reason, craft oriented souvenirs are respected as intimate pieces transferring the soul of their places of origin.

The paper aims to investigate the condition of the souvenir market and the place of craft items in two Turkish destinations particularly known for belief tourism, namely Hacibektas and Konya. These two centers are known for having been the dwelling places of two holy persons whose dates and places of birth—Persia—were close, and both of whom migrated to Anatolia as a result of the Mongolian conquests. The lodges founded by these two saints hosted craft guilds particular to the regions. The stone guild of Hacibektas and felt guild of Konya gave rise to a certain tradition, which lasted until recently. This study aims to make a comparison between these two cities with respect to the local conditions and touristic potential.

THE SOUVENIR AS A DISTINCT PRODUCT CATEGORY

Culture is bundled up with business services, leisure industries and tourism in an effort to regenerate city-regions and therefore create wealth and employment (Booth and Boyle, 1993 referred by Julier, 2008). While cultural industries contribute to the identity of a space by creating a more dynamic, creative and enterprising population, they also provide the designer with a dynamic status in the entrepreneurial culture. Designers, as the signifiers of modernity, contribute to an urban center's national and international promotion with their skills in participating in commercial networks and technical know-how (Julier, 2008). The design act carried out for such a promotion involves graphics, items and services for tourists in general. Souvenirs appear as the particular items created for those tourists.

Souvenirs are reminders of a particular time, location or attraction and are generally associated with a touristic act or a ceremony. These generally unbranded items appear as a unique product category that operate as agents that commoditize a province. According to Gordon, souvenirs are classified as "pictorial images" such as postcards; "pieces of the rock" such as sea shells collected from nature; "symbolic shorthand"

such as the icons particular to any space that, in time, were turned into mass produced gadgets, "markers" like the printed t-shirts and "local products" whose material and production are indigenous to the area (1986). The important attributes of souvenirs are product value (range, quality), product display characteristics (color, display, packaging, size), and uniqueness (Turner, Reisinger, 2001). However, the expanding interest in such unique pieces brings together the increase in production and popularization that lead to decreased authenticity.

Tourism is an economic act, which emerged with the need to travel in order to seek out new experiences and ways of life. The tourists who experience alienation through their daily working lives pursue authenticity through their journeys and holidays to return home with an experience of a more primitive or alternative lifestyle (Litrell, Anderson, Brown, 1993). The authentic experience of this alternative lifestyle is identified and carried to real life via the souvenirs. The term authenticity is generally taken as a concept of reproduction of the realness belonging to the other. It is a conceptualization of an elusive, inadequately defined, other cultural, socially ordered genuineness (Spooner, 1986). Authenticity is a socially constructed interpretation of the realness of the objects. Namely, authentic experiences come from constructed reality by beliefs, attitudes and powers, not from inherent realness (Cohen, 1988). Authenticity is regarded as a child of old-fashioned exoticism using the forms and styles of a supposedly homogenous and unbroken tradition (Rushdie, 1991, as cited by Taylor, 2001: 7).

Time spent during the visit to sacred spaces is regarded to be sacred too. Accordingly, the souvenirs bought during these visits are also regarded as sacred. These souvenirs also operate as tools to strengthen traditional religious practices. As items particular to faith-based design, these objects are either traditional items used in religious rituals, or items onto which faith-specific ornaments, slogans or forms are applied (Gorman, 2009). While handwork operates as the tool to sanctify a gift (Belk et.al, 1989), traditional crafts become one of the primary components in sacred souvenirs. Moreover, as a reminder of a trip to a holy place, craft based souvenirs are regarded as being much more holy. But the fact is that the souvenir market is dominated by mass-produced cheap items, in general, due to the high cost of craft based production or the disappearance of traditional crafts.

TWO CENTERS FOR BELIEF TOURISM

In order to trace the impact of craft on the souvenir market in holy places, two towns in Turkey particular for belief tourism were selected. In these two towns, there are two lodges that serve as the centers for two sects specific to Anatolia. These two lodges were founded on relatively close dates and by two saints Haji Bektash-i Veli and Mawlana Jalaeddin-i Rumi. Born on dates and cities—in Khorasan, Persia—close to each other, they both migrated to Anatolia escaping from the Mongolian conquests. The doctrine of these two saints formed the two roots in morality of the Anatolian population. Moreover, traditional Turkish music is said to be rooted in the music

of these two sects: Bektashi music is regarded as the origin of Turkish folk music, whereas Mewlevi music is the base of traditional classical Turkish music. These two lodges are located in Hacibektas (a town belonging to the city of Nevsehir) and Konya. After the foundation of the Turkish Republic, all of the lodges were closed and today the aforementioned lodges serve as museums.

Hacibektas

Hacibektas is a town in the city of Nevsehir, with a population of 11.700. As a typical central Anatolian town, the source of income is generally agriculture and stockbreeding. Onyx mining used to be one of the main branches of business, but this has been discontinued over the last 20 years. Stonework is also linked with Bektashi mythology and the first stone guild is said to be founded in the Bektashi lodge.

Haji Bektash-i Veli, the founder of the Bektashi lodge in this town, was born in 1209 in Nishapur of Khorasan, Persia and died in 1271 in Hacibektas. With the impact of the Mongolian conquests in the region, he migrated to Anatolia and settled in Sulucakarahoyuk, which was then given the name Hacibektas. His doctrine is regarded to have adapted the Shamanic Turkic belief system to Islam with certain respect for nature.

Recently, the region's potential for tourism has been supported by Cappadocia: a near-by tourist destination and a sacred site for Christians. Every year commemoration ceremonies are held in August for Haji Bektash-i Veli. The lodge, which is turned into a museum, is visited by 450.000 tourists every year and 10.000 of them are international tourists that stopover in Cappadocia (interview with Taylan Sümer, 2013). Today, Hacibektas is one of the destinations visited in Cappadocia tours. However, the meaning of the province changes for domestic and international tourists. For international tourists, Hacibektas is a minor destination visited in only a few hours. For domestic tourists, however, the province is the primary destination visited by faith tourists.

Konya

Konya, the capital of the Anatolian Seljuk state between 1076-1277, is known today as an agriculture and industry center and one of the important destinations for belief tourism. The city center with a population of 1.100.000 is the 7th largest city in Turkey and together with its counties has the largest area survey.

As a center for belief tourism, the city is known for the Mewlevi lodge founded by Mawlana Jalaladdin Rumi. Mawlana was born in 1207 in Belkh, Khorasan, Persia and passed away in 1273 in Konya. Similar to Haci Bektash, he left Khorasan because of the Mongolian conquests and settled in the Seljuk capital Konya with his father, one of the era's eminent mutasavvifs. After his father's demise, Mawlana filled in for him and built a remarkable reputation as a person of knowledge and wisdom (Efe, 2013).

Every year, in memory of Mawlana, vuslat ceremonies are held on the 17th of December, the date Mawlana passed away. The

lodge welcomes about 2.000.000 visitors a year and about 1.500.000 of them are domestic tourists (interview with Yasar Sarican, 2014).

SOUVENIR, CRAFT AND BELIEF TOURISM

Recent state of the market

As destinations particular for belief tourism, both Hacibektas and Konya have a marketplace for souvenir items. The market is dominated by symbolic shorthand and local products whose production is not limited to the region. Moreover, some items are imported goods produced in China or Afghanistan as demanded by the local market.

The difference in scale of these two cities is very much reflected in the souvenir market of both. As a small town with a population of about 12.000, and with a 450.000 visitors a year, Hacibektas has a modest market which mainly depends on stonework. In that sense, the range of products is homogeneous with respect to the range in Konya. As an industrial zone, Konya is able to operate international contacts and host diverse production activities ranging from the food industry to plastics. As a reflection of such a vibrant medium, the souvenir market in Konya does not reflect a homogenous craft based character. The craft items are diversified, local products come from different parts of Turkey, and Chinese low-cost products appear as a strong competitor to the local products.

Craftwork in Hacibektas is limited to stonework and has thus allowed stonework to become one of the markers of the region. The local resource, namely onyx stone, refers to Shamanic Turkish mythology as well as the Bektashi faith. As an extension of the mountain cult in shaman-Turkish mythology, stone is regarded to be sacred and is transformed into a symbol of the homeland. At the same time, and as a part of the feminine asset of the Turkic-shaman mountain cult, it became the symbol of fertility. The mountain, as the axis guarding the balance of the world, and the place nearest to God, was believed to engulf the sun every evening and give birth to it again on every morning. The ageless mythological asset called Babal, the possessor of the stones, is regarded to be another component of the stone cult. Babal is believed to reserve a weightless and invisible stone for each newborn to hang around its neck. As the infant grows up and dies, the stone falls from his neck. Anyone who finds this stone is believed to live long and know everything (Bayat, 2007).

Onyx accessories such as the stone of surrender and kanberiyye were eminent components of Bektashi dervish attire (figure 1). Today, these components have been turned into souvenirs to an extent; however, they do not dominate the whole market. Onyx items for daily use such as candleholders or other tabletop objects are very common in the souvenir market (figure 2). Rather than shaping the item around religion, the faith content is attached to products by applying motives particular to the Bektashi faith. Some calligraphic depictions are applied onto the selected items by the souvenir shop owners on customer

Figure 1. Bektashi dervish attire with stone of surrender, palheng and kanberiyye

Figure 2. Onyx items

demand during purchase (figure 3). Some products seem to have been stripped of their faith-based content and made into decorative items. For example, the elliptic "kanberiyye" stone, which is a part of the dervish attire, was turned into an onyx egg to refer to the stone's symbol of fertility (figure 4). Other faith-based depictions are observed to be produced as accessories that are minimized in size (figure 5).

Other than onyx items, the market welcomes pictorial images, holograms, silver accessories and carpets. The local onyx

Figure 3. Calligraphy applied on onyx plate

products were distributed to other tourist-destination provinces of Turkey about 35 years ago. However, the increasing production costs resulted in a decrease in mining and production (Akbulut, 2013).

The market in Konya offers a diverse range of souvenirs, which—as a result of the varied modes of production and access to business relations—can be imported and produced locally. The main crafts are felt making and ceramics and reed flute making and wood painting are also popular. Reed flutes are used particularly in Mewlevi music. On the other hand, the wooden spoons decorated with Mewlevi figures such as whirling dervishes or the lodge operate as the pictorial images (figure 6).

Felt and ceramic items appear to be dominant craft pieces in the market. Ceramics are either from domestic or Chinese producers (figure 7). Beginning in 2003, knickknacks in the shape of whirling dervishes began to be imported from China and these low-cost figures with slanting eyes invaded the market. There are also abstract dervish figures made by ceramic artists settled in Konya (figure 8).

There are unique pieces to be found in felt making also. Felt refers back to nomadic Turkish tradition and Mewlevi philosophy. Similar to Bektashi dervish attire, felt caps are indispensable components of Mewlevi dervish attire (figure 9). While traditional production methods have changed over the past 20 years, the products varied and the craft gained currency.

Figure 4. Onyx eggs inspired from kanberiyeye of dervish attire

Figure 5. Faith-based depictions turned into accessories

The range of felt souvenirs varies from accessories (necklace, fibula, handbag, purse, scarf), to garments (hats, jackets), to parts of dervish attire (sikke or caps) (figure 10) and decorative items (wall panels, covers) (figure 11).

Besides ceramics, Chinese products include mechanical items. The whirling dervish is a characteristic form for Konya and is very much used in music boxes and clocks (figure 12). Such items provide a fair like atmosphere to the souvenir market with their sound and kinetic images.

Figure 6. decorated wooden spoons

Figure 7. Ceramic knickknacks in the form of whirling dervishes, from China. Glass varieties in the middle row.

Figure 8. Some examples of local ceramics

Figure 9. Mewlevi dervish attire

Figure 10. Felt mini-cap production in workshop

Figure 11. Felt items

Figure 12. Clocks with whirling dervish

Master's attachment

In the case of belief tourism, craft is generally linked with a province's natural resources. Especially in the case of Hacibektas and Konya, craft is linked spiritually to the lodges. In Hacibektas, the stone guild, and in Konya the felt guild were first founded in the lodges. Both of the crafts and materials (stone and felt) are linked with the belief system and few remaining masters are still sentimentally attached to the order of the lodge.

The craft masters interviewed appear to be born into crafts families and trained by relatives. The craft descends from father to son. However, due to the financial circumstances, the masters appear to alternate between other means of income generation at some stages of their lives. However, this does not mean a total separation from the craft. After trying other occupations, some return to the craft or the craft becomes a side occupation alongside a job providing stable income. For example, Hüseyin Gökçe, a former stonemaster who is cur-

rently an officer in museum in Hacibektas, switches to craft-work, at a particular time of year in order to help his family's small scale souvenir production for the ceremonies in August.

The craftsmen generally experience tension between creative self-expression and the need to conform to societal demands and financial realism (Ranson, 1989). The interviewed masters are found to be involved with the production of traditional items at the beginning such as felt covers, dervish caps or stones of surrender. Today, these masters appear not to follow classical patterns of production due to the changing market conditions. First of all, the classical items that were produced by the fathers of these masters are generally of no use today. Traditionally, felt is used to make covers for the traditional sofas called *divan*, or the shakedown, or as shepherds' garments. Felt master Celallettin Berberoğlu started making felt with his grandfather and father by making such kind of items. In the 1990s, he decided to search for alternative ways of using the fabric and therefore began making souvenirs such as pendants, scarves, and other decorative items. Today, he also runs a felt training program in his workshop. The stonemaster Deniz Ulutaş in Hacibektas, shifted to gravestone and workbench production because of the souvenir market's low profit margins. However, his family is known to be the leading souvenir producer in the town.

The masters are very much involved with the mystic content of the craft and the material. Felt, for example, is a reflection of the Mewlevi understanding of the human being according to Celallettin Berberoğlu, who is a whirling dervish at the same time:

"... wool and the human being are both going through a process of purification. The wool must be lambswool, not the sheep's, and it should meet with a piece of water in order to become felt. The master kneads that wool in a straw mat. Then, the master flattens the wool under his feet with the same rhythmic breathing and pronouncing the sound "huh". Actually, hu is the manifestation of God, and what is being stamped on is the ego of the human being, everything that we are not but we think we are; status, money, fame, everything. The master is the mentor and he knows the state of the wool in the mat without seeing it. And when the mat is opened, we meet with a texture that shrunken. The shrunken element becomes firmer, the one behaving modestly, grows..." (2014)

Moreover, the traditional forms with religious content are regarded to be immune elements whose production should be restricted to the region. In the souvenir market in Hacibektas, most of the items appear to be produced in Afghanistan where production costs are minimal. However, religious forms such as the surrender stone are still made in the town. Deniz Ulutaş, the stone master, strongly opposes the idea of carrying the production of the surrender stone to Afghanistan:

"... The Afghan knows nothing about the stone of surrender, no, they cannot make it." (2013)

The question of authenticity

Craft is an element that transfers the holiness of a place to its souvenirs. It is also a manifestation of authenticity in souve-

nirs for tourists. Objective authenticity can be defined as an experience which genuinely samples the culture of the other; that is, the host society and the host people (Hillman, 2012:2). As typical tourists' travel motivations include such things as social status, cultural enrichment, and learning new things, experiencing a foreign destination successfully works with such souvenirs that remind people of their trips (Swanson, Horridge, 2006).

However, objects are not the sole elements that transfer authenticity; this can also be done through shows and hands on experiences. The question is whether these "staged experiences" supported by a "staged authenticity" meet with the tourists' motivation for genuine, spontaneous and authentic experience and to see real life as it is. The artificial settings created for the tourists serve as a front stage where a 'false reality' for show and performance is constructed (Hillman, 2012). As a result, the souvenirs appear as the reminders of these staged experiences created through staged authenticity.

In both cases, the tourists are provided with a holy dance show: *semah* in Hacibektas and *sema* in Konya. For destinations peculiar for belief tourism, craft does not appear as a primary attraction, but the craft's link with the belief is generally provided with the souvenir items. These items are generally components of the dervish attire: the stone of surrender in Hacibektas and the felt *sikke* (cap) in Konya, the material is attributed mystic characteristics.

The souvenirs that are originally parts of dervish attire, such as surrender stones or dervish caps, can be regarded as elements of staged authenticity. The tourist purchasing such items will not be involved in a religious act involving the items, but the items are kept as the reminders of the trip and the holy nature of the region. This holy characteristic is transferred to other souvenirs for daily use with the craft or the material specific to the region. For example, the holy stone is used to make sugar bowls, ashtrays, candleholders, etc. or the lodge's craft, namely felt making, is popular in textile and accessory production.

Augmenting the province's touristic potential with hands-on craft shows is a hot debate in Hacibektas. In Cappadocia, which is a popular touristic destination close to Hacibektas, the tourists are provided with a ceramic production experience in which they are able to sit on a turn bench and play with mud. The stone masters in Hacibektas tend to adapt such an experience to stone workshops in order to attract more tourists and to resurrect the production of stone items in the region.

Authenticity in such regions is impaired by the transgression of certain items peculiar to certain places. One of the well-known souvenirs of Konya is the bergamot-flavored candy known as Mewlana candy. Recently, this item is also being produced as "Hacibektas candy" and sold in the Hacibektas souvenir market (Figure 13). Another example is that of rose scented beads produced in Isparta (Figure 14). Such items with religious references can hold a place in the souvenir market without the need to be authentic.

Figure 13. Transgressive candy

CONCLUSION

Craft, as the local production act depending on indigenous resources, is a particular element for the souvenir market in tourist sites. The authenticity of a souvenir is very much supported by local businesses and crafts. It occupies a particular place in belief tourism as craftwork is regarded to be the sole element to sanctify a gift. However, it is not supported much by the souvenir market and high production costs and the decreasing number of craft masters forces the market to shift to mass produced and even kitsch items.

The selected regions were particular for belief tourism with lodges particular to craft guilds. The souvenir markets in these regions are studied with respect to the craft activity particular to the regions and the lodges. As a matter of fact, the souvenir market is observed to present a false reality in either craft based items or mass-produced ones.

The faith origin of the craft and the material is hardly recognizable in the market. Although the craft masters are sentimentally attached to their belief, they hardly survive with traditional modes of production and are forced to shift alternative modes or sources of income. The souvenir market appears as a means for the craft to survive, but the false reality of the souvenir embraces the danger of breeding corrupt variations of traditional forms. On the other hand, the traditional faith based forms are generally observed to be miniaturized and rendered into functional items or accessories such as necklaces, key rings etc. So the belief content is transformed into daily life.

Intense industry in Konya is reflected in the souvenir market by inhibiting it from demonstrating a craft based character. The souvenirs are from different cities, countries, materials and origins. In such a circumstance, the souvenir market is dominated by certain forms of whirling dervishes, the depictions of the Mevlevi lodge or calligraphic pieces. On the other hand, the scarcity of resources in Hacibektas results in a modest and homogenous market dominated by onyx items. However this homogenous structure offers a void market behind it; the production act together with the source of onyx is partly based in the town.

Figure 14. Scented beads of Isparta in Konya souvenir shops

Unfortunately, the traditional crafts are about to disappear. It is not easy for the few remaining masters to find apprentices to take over the craft. The education programs offered by public training centers cannot survive due to lack of interest. As felt is a textile-based material, it has recently become popular among women. Stonework, on the other hand, is scarce given that it requires heavy machinery and raw material. Certain models such as hands on craft practice shows are thought to be adapted to rejuvenate stone mastery in the region. Another way to raise interest in craft can be through publicity as it can act to emphasize the crafts' faith based origin. Linking the material and craft with the spirituality of the region enhances awareness and results in a souvenir market without corruption.

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SHARED VALUE AS A CONTRIBUTOR TO SOCIAL INNOVATION

Case study: The Universidad de los Andes and its surrounding entrepreneurial environment.

María de los Ángeles González Pérez

Associate Professor, Universidad de los Andes – Team Member, *Emprende* Program

✉ marigonz@uniandes.edu.co

Freddy Zapata Vanegas

Associate Professor, Universidad de los Andes – Team Member, *Emprende* Program

✉ fzapata@uniandes.edu.co

Javier Francisco Silva Salazar

Methodological Advisor – Team Member, *Emprende* Program

✉ blife@busineslifemodel.com

Santiago Restrepo Barrera

Methodological Advisor – Team Member, *Emprende* Program

ABSTRACT

The creation of networks involving different stakeholders in a community promotes an ideal environment for the development of shared value towards social innovation. The *Emprende* Program is a course targeting 16 neighborhood businesses which are connected with the Universidad de los Andes, Bogotá. Among other objectives, the program aims to develop entrepreneurial skills such as problem identification, risk taking and team work. Such skills respond to changes in urban landscapes and challenges from new competitors.

The program's methodologies combine analytical and design thinking. The program consisted of sessions that involved participatory work, observation, creativity, and management. Prototype development is an integrative mechanism for team work, network creation, and the skills appropriation skills. All of these aspects are key to the development of shared value and the fostering of social innovation.

Finally, the program fostered skills among small-scale entrepreneurs and enabled them to transform their practice, thus promoting the creation of social capital by instilling deeper levels of awareness both of their own roles and of their environments.

KEY WORDS: *shared value, social innovation, social networks, business model, design thinking.*

INTRODUCTION

The Progresia Fenicia Project and the Emprende Program

By observing and identifying the results of behaviors and interactions among individuals and communities involved in projects aimed at fostering innovation, entrepreneurship and competition, the program moves the discussion beyond questions of science and technology, becoming a laboratory for testing actions that lead to social innovation.

In social innovation, solutions to problems do not lie only in the production and accumulation of wealth. The key re-

sides in fact in creating sustainable changes in people's lives (Juarez, 2009). For the *Emprende* Program¹, these changes also involve companies and organizations creating shared value by making connections that are capable of enhancing the performance of individuals within communities, contributing in this way to economic, social, environmental, and geopolitical development.

The *Las Aguas* neighborhood of Bogotá D.C, in which the Universidad de los Andes is located, is of great significance

1. Translator's note: the Spanish word *Emprende* is a second person imperative of the verb *emprender*. In this context it conveys the idea of encouraging individuals or companies to develop as entrepreneurs.

for the development of the city center; the neighborhood is, in addition, part of an urban renewal project. The *Progresía Fenicia* project was created under the leadership of the Universidad de los Andes in response to these circumstances in the area of *Las Aguas* known as the *Triángulo de Fenicia*. Its objective is to develop projects that have a high impact on the surrounding space and to encourage transformation, innovation, and sustainability in the area.

The project operates according to three strategic priorities:

- People as stakeholders and subjects of transformation.
- Activities (i.e., work, production, sales) carried out in the zone as engines of change and to improve living conditions.
- Urban landscapes emerging from public and private spaces to ensure the interaction of interests and the creation of collective identity.

Emprende emerged in 2012 on the initiative of *Progresía Fenicia*'s leadership group, with the objective of promoting entrepreneurial activities in the area. The main goal was to improve the economic and social conditions of small businesses in the vicinity of the university by following an approach that was intended to empower businesses to adopt more productive and innovative practices.

Among the achievements expected of the small-scale entrepreneurs were: the ability to identify new opportunities and solve problems affecting their businesses; create spaces for collaborative creation (co-creation) where each could share their experiences and learning; and develop teamworking abilities which would enable them to make good decisions, take risks, develop communication skills and take ownership of ideas, concepts, and processes.

Based on these practices for better entrepreneurship, the project sought to develop efficient business models organized according to three axes: new value propositions, understanding customer needs and business strengthening to ensure long term sustainability. Tools including observation, creativity, and management were applied in practical exercises with entrepreneurs, alongside theoretical concepts, thus promoting interaction and value creation.

The program was developed through three modules:

- The first module, “Yes, I have a product and a client”, focused on developing and consolidating the entrepreneurial project by emphasizing product delivery and interaction between entrepreneurs and customers.
- The second, called “Yes, I have a business”, focused on the importance of entrepreneurs understanding their own business model: efficient intake and output of resources, and understanding of process flow (the value chain).
- The last module, “Yes, I am sustainable” sought to secure the sustainability businesses through the formalization in long term and establishment of strategic partnerships.

32 small-scale entrepreneurs from 16 neighborhood businesses participated in the first phase of the program².

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2. 7 restaurants, 4 copying and Internet venues, 1 store, 1 super-market, 1 hospice, and 1 woodshop.

The program team consisted of professionals from the faculties of Administration, Architecture and Design at the Universidad de los Andes. In the beginning, the concept of creating shared value was not explicit either for the entrepreneurs or the university staff. The concept became visible during the course, which consequently achieved more than had originally been foreseen when its objectives were set. The initial situation created an ideal environment for generating knowledge and envisioning broader horizons for the social and economic components of the businesses involved in the project, introducing the concept of shared value to the community and to its productive activities.

THE EMPRENDE PROGRAM AND SHARED VALUE

The creation of networks, here understood as the promotion of partnerships between different stakeholders in the same community, promotes the development of shared value. As argued by Porter & Kramer (2011, p.5) “Shared value creation focuses on identifying and expanding the connections between societal and economic progress. In addition to reconciling the interaction between society and corporate performance”.

From its inception, *Emprende* has sought to impact on each of the stakeholders, in addition to promoting deeper social interactions between them by encouraging the performance of tangible and intangible economic activities. These activities contributed to the creation of new value networks as a result of the shared experiences of stakeholders. Porter & Kramer (2011, p. 5) identify three key ways in which companies can create shared value by: “reconceiving products and markets, redefining productivity in the value chain, and building supportive industry clusters at the company’s locations”. From this perspective, *Emprende* fulfills the task of giving entrepreneurs basic guidelines regarding these concepts, while proposing changes in their thinking as individuals and developing a collective, community-oriented mindset.

The first module enabled the entrepreneurs to consider and act upon the needs and benefits concerning their value proposal from different perspectives. This new way of thinking about products, services and customers had a great impact on the stakeholders from the business environment.

The second module prompted understanding and conceptualization of a value chain and helped define added value in products and services by identifying the characteristics of market sectors and profiles. It thus provided entrepreneurs with guidelines for understanding and helped them re-think and model new proposals.

Finally, the third module envisioned opportunities for developing local clusters by building on the skills and networks developed by small-scale entrepreneurs. While such skills and networks did not exist at the beginning of the program, they came to represent a potential space for the creation of shared value.

We took the findings and difficulties that emerged during our work with the businesses as references to validate the concept of shared value within the program. In addition, we sought to establish a range of relationships, encouraging the development of internal networks within the work teams and external ones between entrepreneurs and the university.

INTERNAL NETWORKS AND DESIGN THINKING

A network is a strategic mechanism which integrates individuals and actions under a structure of interests, trust, and reciprocity (Becerra, 2008). Networks involve learning and innovation. As Tracy and Clack, 2003 (cited in Becerra, 2008) have pointed out, networks promote interactive learning in organizations through the sharing of knowledge and information, permitting the construction of values and new work models.

The development of networks is the product of the relation between two principal kinds of opportunity that promote the development of networks: first, a driver which motivates collaboration during the development of social capital and, second, interventions intended to act on restrictions or voids, which create opportunities for establishing new connections (Galaskiewicz y Wasserman 1981; Meriden, 1985; Kogut et al., 1994, cited by Walker, 1997).

Innovation creates differential value in relation to existing situations. It should thus be understood as a systematic process involving complementary acts of integration between people, elements, and actions. In the case of *Emprende*, we integrated innovation into a methodology based on design thinking, emphasizing in particular the creative nature of every part of the process. Thus, analytical and design thinking were integrated, both becoming mutually complementary. While scientists research phenomena in order to discover elements and patterns, designers create new patterns and concepts, which make it easier to deal with new possibilities (Owen, 2006). In addition, design thinking leads to innovation that is centered on people and experiences, creating new relationship systems and cultivating a cutting edge culture and processes based on discipline in which, as Kumar (2013) argues,

individuals draw on real life situations, observing, iterating³ and learning from them.

Observing, iterating, and learning are key aspects of the creative process because groups need to gain experience and knowledge through hypothesis-testing focused on problem solving⁴.

In practice, design thinking revolves around two axes, discussed by Beckman and Barry (2007). One is based on the interplay between the rational and the practical, another moves between the real and abstract. These axes inform the development of the four stages of design thinking: the first stage as Discovering, the second stage as Interpreting, the third stage as Deciding, and the fourth stage as Solving.

Emprende's methodology applies the principles of design thinking to all three of the modules discussed above (Figure 1). Negotiating the four stages means that planning must involve processes of both divergent and convergent thought. Divergent thought works with creative, unstructured processes that involve a high level of uncertainty. Convergent thought works with processes which are analytical, rational, and synthesis oriented (Owen, 2005 y Beckman & Barry, 2007).

The first and the second stages make reference to the observation module (see Figure 2). Jointly with the entrepreneurs we identified aspects that were specific to their respective businesses: their product and/or service and the market. Similarly, entrepreneurs were presented with potential future scenarios, which allowed them to envision a “rational business

3. Martin (2006) describes abductive reasoning as a process of modeling an exploratory hypothesis as the only logical operation likely to introduce new ideas. Martin cites Pierce (1905, in turn cited by Hoffman, 1995).
4. According to Dunne & Martin (2006) this aspect relates to abductive thought, responding in a creative and propositional manner to restrictive situations. This aspect is advantageous in processes. That is, traditional inductive and deductive thinking are integrated within it, as inductive thinking generalizes from a specific case, while deductive thinking makes inferences based on logical premises.

Figure 1. Program Modules and Method for Design Thinking

Figure 2. Design thinking methodology- stages and modules

model⁷⁵. These models included tangible brand concepts that were tested by developing small-scale “prototypes”, tested in the classroom and in business premises before being tested out on a larger scale.

The results of this business model inscribed the individual ideas of each business based on their knowledge and experience. This model did not prove to be very much different from the other proposals for value in similar businesses.

The second and third stages were directed toward the creative module creation. Results were analyzed according to the model of “creative and strategic business” (see Figure 3). The “creative business model” uses divergent thinking to envision the rational business model from divergent and novel perspectives

5. Rational business model (descriptive model of information and understanding of the processes that currently occur in the business), creative business model (divergent iteration model that facilitates obtaining answers and unexpected items, hard to find using conventional conservative and dynamic processes) and strategic business model (converged business model, test results information of the predecessor models, which allows the user/entrepreneur to obtain differentiating findings and results for execution time).
The rational, creative and strategic business models are part of the methodology used in the course “Product 4 (Product strategy)”, taught by the Design program at the Universidad de los Andes.

in order to gain differentiation and create value within the multiple aspects which make up the business environment.

Results were analyzed according of “the creative and strategic business model” (see Figure 3). The creative Business model tool uses divergent thinking to envision the rational business model from divergent and novel perspectives in order to gain differentiation and create value within the multiple aspects which make up the business environment.

The strategic business model emerges as a result of this process. It responds to the dynamics of convergent thinking and rational and structured business logic, without losing the advantageous aspects of the creative model.

The third and fourth stages were associated with management and demonstration modules. The creative outcomes with small-scale entrepreneurs and potential partners became more visible during these stages. Outcomes were presented to a group of experts and professionals (Events 1 & 2) in order to obtain their feedback on the value proposals, curves, service mapping and routes, and service experiences within the different businesses.

Feedback gathered during these events set the scene for each of the *Emprende Program* modules that were introduced subsequently. These operated according to established timelines for the development of sessions, workshops, and assignments.

Figure 3. Types of business models in the methodology

Prototype value and network building

When it is applied, design thinking takes into account the principles of interdisciplinary work, uncertainty, and complexity. Building prototypes as a strategy enabled us to address these principles and also to build networks and work teams; which contributed to the development and management of the program.

In the classroom, we implemented workshops for developing prototypes intended to help consolidate businesses. For this purpose we used the Business Life (BL) tool. This tool, which is designed to visualize information and concepts, allowed us to organize the workshop components and establish relations between them in creative ways, thus facilitating novel business strategies and configurations.

The dynamic of the workshops using the BL tool (see Figure 4) promoted interactions between people, relying on their particular skills and knowledge. Hence, from the initial definition of the prototype⁶ we developed and co-created proposals emerging from the creative model while in the creative and management dimensions we used the strategic model.

The workshop results were enhanced with support from the work team and students from the Design and Administration faculties. The students joined the program during its third stage, contributing to the development of the prototypes and the differentiation of proposals, which were implemented in a project that integrated academic work and everyday business. As entrepreneur Sanchez, owner of the restaurant *Merotacos*, affirmed:

“Confidence (...) was key (...): knowing that the program was not just teaching me a traditional course, but that they were in my establishment, observing my work and my shortcomings”. Daza,

6. Here, understood as the design of a work model intending to test product and service concepts associated with relationships between customers and suppliers.

C. (producer) (2013). *Closing Video for Empreder*. Bogota: Media Workshop, Architecture and Design faculty.

With regards to the rational, creative, and strategic business models we implemented, we worked with prototypes and pilots, including typologies such as: entry tests, fast prototypes, concept testing and association pilots, all of which are discussed by Murray, R. Caulier-Grice, J. & Mulgan, G. (2010).

Based on the prototypes developed within the creative dimension, we drew on the value proposal developed in collaboration with the individual entrepreneur during observation. The value proposals were initially developed on the basis of the rational business model, organized according to the components, which individual entrepreneurs identified as relevant to their business from a logical and foundational perspective. The entrepreneurs received support from the team during the analysis and inventory process; this exercise was framed within entry tests prototyping typology.

Figure 4. The Business Life Model Tool

For the creative business model we used concept prototypes that promoted creativity (see photo 1). During this exercise we observed the ways in which the entrepreneurs understood the rational model based on new interpretations of images (collage⁷) thus identifying relationships and narratives, which had not previously been noticed. Such was the case of a business called, the *Casetica de la Esquina* (the Corner Hut), where two young women managed to project their business towards different areas of the market, transforming themselves from street vendors into a specialized business selling necessities for university women⁸.

The prototypes were intended to provide a sense of psychological freedom and security⁹. The workshop provided an environment, which was not influenced by external judgments that might have inhibited the free expression of participants' proposals. As Landau argues (1987), such an environment of acceptance and trust strengthens bonds of friendship and empathy. Project members Beltrán, J., Londoño, S., Neira, C. & Raffo, A. expressed this as follows in their report on their work with entrepreneurs (13 December de 2013):

"We kept in permanent contact with the owners of Shawarma. That was our greatest achievement in making their ideas concrete. We believe this is essential for co-creation. Developing a friendship with entrepreneurs helped us create empathy and increase the flow of ideas and team productivity".

The entrepreneurs began the program with the expectation of transforming their businesses and, since motivation is a key driver of the creativity required to meet unsatisfied needs, this enabled an effective creative model to be developed. Finally, fast prototypes and association pilots were developed for the Management and Demonstration axes, as a means of achieving a strategic business model. Fast prototypes required immediate implementation capable of speeding up the learning process and possible applications of the new ideas (Murray, R., Caulier-Grice, J. & Mulgan, G., 2010). In this case, the entrepreneurs absorbed the theoretical model in a natural and spontaneous way. Activities focused on the aspects of identity and branding (logo, packaging, service goals and design of interior spaces). In their report Beltrán, J., Londoño, S., Neira, C. & Raffo, A. (13 de December of 2013) added:

"The San Isidro practice experience demonstrates the importance of establishing the role of the designer within a co-creation exercise. Development by entrepreneurs of their prototype was very autonomous, and our work consisted mainly in guiding them through the process with very minor contributions".

7. A creative technique of registering and visualizing using image clippings and random headlines from newspapers and magazines; its purpose is to create new narratives and imaginaries.
8. Value proposal: "The *Casetica de la Esquina* offers products for basic care, targeting young women who want immediate well-being solutions on a daily basis. We also provide accessories, beauty products, diet snacks and candy for healthy cravings", Universidad de los Andes, 2013.
9. Understanding psychological freedom as an attitude that enables individuals to playfully manage perceptions, concepts, and meanings; whereas, security is achieved through self-confidence and acceptance (Landau, 1987).

Photo 1. Creative Business Model

Photo 2. Strategic Business Model. Event 1: Value proposal

Photo 3. Strategic Business Model. Event 1: Communication skills

Fast prototypes enabled us to envision and realize better practices for consolidating the strategic business model, which culminated with the demonstrations in Event 1: value proposal and Event 2: potential partners (see photos 2, 3, 4 and 5).

For their part, *association pilots* were conducted with larger scale prototypes. Through visualizations created using the BL tool, we were able to enhance the value proposal of each business model and its most representative and important components. These components were not only realized through identity and branding, but also in products and service experiences.

In this program, we built shared value through the identification of needs and challenges for the development of both the Universidad de los Andes and the community. Here, people are the motivation and engine of social innovation, through their interactions, just as human centered design is to design thinking.

Though internal networks focused on consolidating the practices of the program within each business's team, the concept of external networks plays a role in the interaction with actors outside of the university.

EXTERNAL NETWORKS AND THE COMMUNITY

An external network involves stakeholders from outside the organization or institution. These networks constitute processes that seek to integrate and facilitate communication between different members of the community; organizations and institutions are the main frame of reference.

During the execution of the program we identified two types of external networks:

1. *Vertical external networks*¹⁰ connected with the university. These emerged from actions that prompted the development of new spaces for the stakeholders involved in the process. They maintained the mutually beneficial relationships created as a result of the process by implementing new dynamics, which strengthen specific interests.
2. *Horizontal external networks*¹¹ created between other members of the community. These are bonds established between businesses, employees, suppliers, residents and customers in order to develop new actions and behaviors, which generate mutual benefit and help businesses, become more competitive as they enter a differential environment. Strategic partnerships enabled the growth of entrepreneurial structures by developing new ways of thinking and interacting (Canel & Mitchell, 2013). For instance, since business owners in the community knew each other, there was a sense of belonging in the community, which provided opportunities for sharing experienc-

10. Those modes of cooperation between companies that are situated in different and consecutive positions within the production chain, aiming to reach competitive advantages they could not achieve individually. The most common example is the establishment of a partnership of strategic stable supply between various client micro and medium companies and their networks and subcontractors and suppliers (Becerra 2008, p. 39).
11. A mode of cooperation between independent companies of comparable size, which produce the same type of goods and decide to join forces in order to market them, buy supplies collectively, or procure common services; or companies that organize together in order to produce a unique product, each of them specializing in different parts and components. Usually, these networks are mainly oriented towards scale economies and greater negotiating power, and they are often made of groups of micro, small, and medium sized companies operating in the same geographical area (Becerra, 2008, p. 39).

es and developing group knowledge about opportunities. They also created social capital and suggested ways to overcome restrictions created by the divergence between the knowledge of individual entrepreneurs and aspects such as the contents of the program, work schedules or economic resources.

The structuring of internal and external networks, and the relationship between them, is essential to establishing a solid basis for the creation of shared value. This is principally because it is possible to draw on these networks to specify the particular conditions that increase participation levels. In this way members grew to enjoy greater access to information on available knowledge and experiences, to cooperate with other members of the network, to grow and increase their levels of responsiveness, ultimately promoting trust and social cohesion.

Through the theoretical and practical exercise conducted as a part of the *Emprende* project we found that there was reciprocity between internal and external networks (see Figure 5), particularly in the interaction between entrepreneurs' venues and the benefits obtained by the university community. As the program moved forward, the participation¹² of different academic areas within the university became more apparent,

12. The environment observation tool designed by Business Life, contributed to the participation of entrepreneurs with other members of the community, including competitors, suppliers, and others.

Photo 4. Strategic Business Model. Event 2: potential partners

Photo 5. Strategic Business Model. Event 2: potential customers

Figure 5. Internal and External Social Network

primarily through the network created with entrepreneurs to help them increase their knowledge and enhance their business models. Similarly, this paved the way for the creation of synergies between the different groups that made up the work teams, entrepreneurs and potential clusters, whose development was discussed at the beginning of the process.

An example of the relationship between networks and value chains in the case of entrepreneurs was provided by the university through the inclusion in the program of business plans presented by *Cintel*¹³ and *Shawarma*¹⁴.

Cintel geared its value proposal towards creating a competitive advantage, strengthening of a waste management culture, and responsible use of electronic devices. They also projected developing partnerships with the university's engineering department.

Shawarma, a carryout restaurant selling food from a window onto the street did not have a space where customers could eat comfortably and in hygienic conditions. This was their

13. *Cintel's* value proposal: "Cintel offers accessories and technical services for electronics repair, specializing in cellphones and tablets. It focuses its attention mainly on the university community, which uses the service on a daily basis. It provides security and confidence to its clients, providing advice and support during the purchase, use, maintenance and repair of the products. Aware of the environmental impact produced by both the parts and the devices, we seek support from the District Secretary of the Environment, CAR, and Eco-Compute in order to fulfil the four "Rs" governing the management of waste from cellphones and tablets: repair, reuse, recycle, and renovate", Universidad de los Andes, 2013.
14. *Shawarma's* value proposal: "Shawarma Rain & Sun is a fast food restaurant. Its preparations mix the delicacies of Middle Eastern food with the flavors of our region. Having limited space, and understanding the needs of students and workers, Shawarma Rain & Sun has created a unique venue providing well-balanced foods. It seeks to promote wellbeing by providing balanced meals for daily life, regardless of the weather and within 70 seconds. Counting on you, we offer Shawarma Sun and, on rainy days, we deliver Shawarma Rain", Universidad de los Andes, 2013.

motivation for joining the value proposal, which provides consumer spaces within the university, reducing the time people on campus need to expend buying food.

The three business models presented in the methodology, the practice sessions in class, the BL tool and, in particular, the events were all triggers that enhanced the capacity of the entrepreneurs and their businesses to cooperate with the university. Response capacity was facilitated by the openness and positive attitudes of some of the entrepreneurs, the recognition and attention that the team paid to their personal and commercial life stories, expectations, future vision, and perceptions about *Las Aguas* area. All of these aspects promoted self-confidence and empowered participating entrepreneurs to face new challenges.

Furthermore, the growing confidence of the entrepreneurs allowed them to partake in the work of others. This was particularly the case as the taking in of knowledge through the experience of the prototypes became a key strategy for creative work. By listening and asking questions, they explored possibilities, discovered alternatives, and recognized other perspectives. Their dialogue empowered their learning and action skills.

Within this scenario, the project achieved a sense of belonging in the program and we were able to share our ideals in a training process for entrepreneurs from the *Triángulo de Fenicia*, a community that had not previously been recognized as such.

CONCLUSIONS

Social innovation and people

As an entrepreneurship and competitiveness project, *Emprende* facilitated the interaction and characterization of the modes of operation of a community and its individuals, thus leading to practices that are key to social innovation. It functioned as an organic process in which people, work elements, and action related in ways that helped establish differential value in relation to existing situations in the business ecosystem.

The synergy developed between internal and external networks provided evidence of the existence of a replicable model of social innovation. Currently, the university is considering a second version of the program and a follow up of the venues included in the first phase in the hope of strengthening the program and being able to measure the results of the social innovation.

Methodology

Using a methodology based on design thinking helped to develop social innovation as individuals developed entrepreneurship skills, empowering themselves, their ideas, and their businesses (in a bottom-up process). Amongst the skills acquired by entrepreneurs the following may be highlighting: risk taking, teamwork, and tackling creative work.

Keeping in mind the working definition of shared value, the methodology was a key means for guiding entrepreneurs towards collaborative work and to develop their understanding of the business environment. Similarly, the creation of networks was the basis for promoting the creation of shared value and clusters.

The use of Business Life tools allowed us to visualize new scenarios for the business model and contributed to the formation of networks and work teams. In the same manner, the prototypes enabled ideas to gain recognition and results to be validated collectively.

Networks and shared value

The networks we identified enabled the participation of stakeholders from the community in social, entrepreneurial, and academic activities, thus creating synergy and strengthening partnerships. In this manner, networks captured and delivered value for businesses, helping them work towards the creation of competitive advantages, which benefited entrepreneurs and the university alike.

Clusters and potential replication

The creation of new external networks prompted the development of local clusters, which belong to a new dimension of interdependence. That is, local businesses developed new relationships with university institutions and their surrounding community, thus promoting an environment of opportunity for the growth of the overall community and the creation of wealth.

Shared value has enhanced the upward mobility of venues by helping them focus on the interests of the university and the needs of the community. Both horizontal and vertical networks balance the relationship between bottom-up and top-down processes of value creation.

Finally, the program provided an opportunity to create networks and shared value, the outcome of both processes being conducive to social innovation. The result was that the community of entrepreneurs from the *Triángulo de Fenicia* was transformed into a potential professional practice network, working to provide social and community development for all of its residents.

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THE CONSTRUCTION OF A COLLECTIVE MEMORY OF URBAN SPACE: EXPLORING THE EXPERIENCES REPORTED BY CYCLISTS IN RECIFE - BRAZIL

William Guedes Lins Júnior
Universidade Federal de Pernambuco - Brazil
✉ william_jr@hotmail.com

Gabriela G. Jesumary
Universidade Federal de Pernambuco - Brazil
✉ gabriela.jesumary@gmail.com

Kátia Medeiros Araújo
Universidade Federal de Pernambuco - Brazil
✉ katia_araujo@hotmail.com

ABSTRACT

This work explores the construction of a collective memory about the meaning and experience of the use of bicycles in the city of Recife, capital of Pernambuco - Brazil. As a demarcation of this research, a Facebook user groups' posts were analyzed. Therefore, this study focuses on the experiences and emotions that relate to processes of urban space appropriation. We used the Sociologist Maurice Halbwachs's Collective Memory theory as the main point of comparison with theoretical reasoning and empirical evidence addressed.

KEYWORDS: *Collective Memory, Experiences, Urban Space, Use of Bicycles, Bikers.*

INTRODUCTION

The recent cycling phenomenon in urban perimeters is associated with movements of international scope such as Critical Mass¹, among others. It is related, in broad terms, with the discussion of urban rights and quality of life in cities, but also has some special features in different social groups and localities where it operates.

In this paper, we explored published posts about the use of bicycles at a specific locus, the city of Recife - Pernambuco State, Brazil. These were considered instruments for exposure and construction of memories in which the bike is evoked as a depository of meaning in the process of urban space appropriation.

The Facebook group surveyed is called *Bicicletada Recife*. It is a "closed" community. Its members seem to be, predomi-

nantly, part of the middle classes² that began to render bicycle use more visible. We consider the group studied a catalyst for the recent growth of the cycling phenomenon in Recife.

We used the universe of posts published in January 2014. The authors of these publications have had their names changed, preserving the gender reference.

This work is the result of a preliminary action of a broader research project. It is the source of two dissertations undertaken by the Design Graduate Program at the Federal University of Pernambuco Program - UFPE.

If the experiences raised through memory³ can be considered the main determinant of identity (Cardoso, 2012) and the decoding of user identity can be considered a tool to support the project, it seems important to explore the memory con-

1 The Massa Crítica (Critical Mass) or "Bicicletada" (term used in many Brazilian cities, in Portugal and Mozambique) is an event and a movement that in many countries, every last Friday of the month, brings together people using human-powered vehicles, including bicycles. It has a horizontal structure and the absence of hierarchy (without leaders or statutes). The first edition of Critical Mass took place in San Francisco in 1992.

2 We adopt a concept, which is distinguished from the Marxist. It serves to "point a group that has similarities in terms of possibilities of purchase (consumption patterns) and a lifestyle composed of some common characteristics, [...], have access to varied sources of information, culture, entertainment and communication (books, television, magazines, internet, cinema, game, museum, etc.), using them" (Guimarães, 2007).

3 "Memory is the experience shifted of its point of departure in the immediate living." (Cardoso, 2012, p. 74)

structured by groups such as *Bicicletada Recife*.

In the first part of the development of this work and in order to support the discussion, we proposed topic about design and memory. Subsequently, the city of Recife is presented as a system. At the same time, Recife is considered as part of another system that the bicycle is also a part of. As a subject, the city seems to be inseparable from the construction of the identity of the *Bicicletada Recife* group. To decode the identity of this group and the meaning assigned to the bike, it is important to know about the city in which it is located. Thus, a description of some conditions and physical characteristics of the city will be given, as well as some properties that can help translate the *modus operandi* and socio-political-cultural nature of it.

We also consider that it is important to make a preliminary classification of the topics covered in the posts published in *Bicicletada Recife*, in order to show their diversity and elect the thematic focus that were made: posts that seem to portray the process of appropriation of the city through the bicycle use.

In this paper, we deal with the concept of Maurice Halbwachs' Collective Memory with the observed empirical evidence. These evidences were presented as transcription posts, in line with a proposal for a netnographic approach.

DESIGN AND MEMORY: AN APPROACH ABOUT EXPERIENCES, ARTIFACTS MEANING AND IDENTITY CONSTRUCTION

One of the Design strategies is to consider user participation in the solution process. When we try to adapt the theoretical framework presented by Löbach, this action can be carried out through the knowledge of the functions. The functions, according to the theory, are attributes that the users relate to the artifacts and that are perceived, especially during the process of using them. The functions given to artifacts are responses to the needs and desires of the user. (Löbach, 2011)

In agreement with Löbach, the needs of the individual are related to physiological prerogatives, psychological sensorial perception conditions, and "spiritual"⁴ determinants. They were associated with the Practical, Aesthetic and Symbolic functions, respectively. (Löbach, 2011)

In order to complement Löbach's proposal, another researcher was taken as a contribution. In an attempt to give effect to the theoretical paradigm adopted by Rafael Cardoso (2012), in the book *Design para um Mundo Complexo* ("Design for a Complex World"), was considered to reveal the identity of the individuals depending on the investigation of the meanings that they assign to the artifacts. To clarify this argument, we adopted "meaning" as: 1. What something is or what it expresses. 2. The importance given to something; value. While we recognize the importance of Löbach's concept on function, we chose to

4 When it allows the man to establish connections with previous experiences and sensations. (Löbach, 2001)

Need – Function Ratio Table

NEED of users	FUNCTIONS attributed to artifacts
Physiological	Practical Function
Psychological of sensorial perception	Aesthetic Function
Spiritual (evocation of past experiences)	Symbolic Function

use the term "meaning" rather than "function" in some of our placements. Therefore, despite the fact that the needs and desires of bike users can be investigated through the relation between the function and the use of bikes, the meanings can be considered as a result of a construction that is independent of the use. Through this perspective, the bike carries meaning for nonusers, although it serves no function for them.

If the meaning that individuals assign to objects is the key to decoding their identity, we can say that the experiences are the premises for the meanings that we attach to objects.

According to Cardoso, experiences are the basis for the construction of an individual's identity. There are those driven directly by the senses and others triggered by memory. This latter embodiment corresponds to indirect experiences; they are the most prevalent and important component of the definition of identity (Cardoso, 2012).

"Most of the experiences we have at our disposal are not accessed at any time by the senses, but through memory. The ability to remember what it was lived or learned and relate to the present situation is the most important mechanism for the establishment and preservation of identity of each" (Cardoso, 2012. P. 73.).

But memories, unlike a computer database, do not simply correspond to the evocation of experiences; they are much more the result of a construction (Cardoso, 2012).

"More than a simple action to recover an experience, memory is a process of reconstruction of the past by confronting the present and by comparison with other parallel experiences. Someone might remember an experience which never had - so-called 'false memory syndrome' - or you can mix your own

experiences with other people and the information acquired by indirect means (conversations, readings, audiovisual media). The memory it is more built rather than accessed [...]” (Cardoso 2012, p.75).

THE CITY, THE BIKE AND THE MEMORY OF CYCLISTS ABOUT THE CITY

We recognize the city as an artifact, since it results from human action to set the material world and, in a dimension of approach, we can understand it as a unit. It is full of functions and practical, aesthetic and symbolic meanings. In the same manner, we assume the city as a system. In this complex⁵ system, artifacts are associated with a set of natural objects and human landscape, all of them interdependent. Through these two perspectives - artifact and / or system - the city can be included in the interest of research design.

Thus, we feel the desire to evoke the memory of cycling and the meanings that can be built on it, in a way that it is considered an indivisible relation between our theme and the theme of city. Recife is subject to usage and meanings and collaborates in the construction of these memories about the bicycles.

This is a complex relationship and a special challenge for a scientific objectification. Especially when we consider a dynamic in which everything is "movement".

For the historian Rafael Cardoso, the meaning of objects is conditioned by six factors; They are related to the material conditions, "use", "environment" and "duration" and to the perception that we have of objects: the "point of view", "speech" and "experience". Cardoso argues that the concept "immovable" should not be applied to the artifacts. (2012) By transferring his argument for our discussion, we can say: both a bicycle and a historic building in a city can be said to be moving, they are mobile.

MATERIAL SITUATION OF A OBJECT	PERCEPTION THAT IS CONSTRUCTED
Use	Point of view
Environment	Speech
Duration	Experience

Finally, we agree that memory as major cause of experiences (Cardoso, 2012), should keep a dimension of the built social phenomenon (Halbwachs, 1990), and represent the confluence of individual dimensions, in which the whole becomes greater than the parts. Users and nonusers of bikes in their capacity as social actors can be understood as immersed in the contexts of culture and their relationships with oth-

5 "[...] Here shall mean a system composed of many elements, layers and structures whose interrelations condition and continually redefine the functioning of the whole." (Cardoso 2012, p. 25).

ers. The socialization of experiences, the life experiences and their emotions are evoked and shared within specific social groups. These collaborate in the construction of meanings of the group, which are kept, processed and disseminated in the face of the "mobility" of all things based on the construction of a collective memory.

RECIFE A SCENARIO FOR THE EMPOWERMENT OF CYCLISTS

Recife is the capital city of the Pernambuco State - Brazil. It is located in the Northeast region, with a warm and humid climate with an average temperature of 25 ° C (77 ° F). According to the census conducted by the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE) in 2010, it has a population of 1,537,704 inhabitants spread over an area of 218.50 km².

Including fourteen towns in the surroundings area (Recife Metropolitan Region), the city corresponds to the fourth largest urban agglomeration in Brazil, with 3.7 million inhabitants. It is the third most densely populated city of the country.

It has 95% of the entire value of the wealth generated from commercial activities and services. Recife estimates 74.5 years (2010) of life expectancy for its inhabitants, has an average income per capita of R\$ 1,144.26 Reais (\$ 480,53 dollars) associated with the Gini index 0.6894 (2010), which is a percentage that indicates very high inequality in income distribution. Its Municipal Human Development Index is 0.772. (2012)

One of the urban characteristics of Recife is the "verticalization", which consists of the construction of numerous large buildings contributing to the constructive densification of some of its regions. This feature, combined with others, has generated tensions between organized civil society, the private and the public sectors. The conflict revolves around issues such as quality of life, ethics and urban rights. Specifically, we highlight tensions involving the lack of roads infrastructure, urban mobility, quality and quantity of public spaces for leisure, playing sports, housing rights and the impact of car-use as the main means of transport. Recife has a high rate of violence. However, it is the Brazilian state capital city that most reduced this rate between 2000 and 2010. The Murder rate is nearly six times higher than that considered acceptable by the UN, but it is lower than that registered in cities such as Detroit and New Orleans in the United States, for example.

The Direitos Urbanos ("Urban Rights") Group (2013) was created as a result of the organized civil society movements. In its blog, this group states that:

"Emerged from the articulation of people interested in politics and concerned with the problems of the city of Recife, from a group of people who knew each other offline, the group has been expanding through social networks and began to turn their concerns into action [...]."

Figure 1. Culture and Leisure Bike Lane, Recife – Brazil.

The Culture and Leisure bike lane⁶ was inaugurated by the government in an unprecedented way at the end of March 2013. On the one hand, in response to an expectation already present in the society, and on the other hand, attending to the goal of promoting bicycle use in the city. In turn, the cycle path was conceived as a point of intersection in the downtown area. The bike lane connects some localities in northern and southern areas of Recife to a preexistent bike path⁷, located in the beach area of the city. It works on Sundays and some holidays from 7 a.m. to 4 p.m. Although bicycle use in Recife was already in place regardless of these paths, especially for low-income workers and students, the creation of this bike lane helped encouraged this practice and the diversification of the debates about the use and meaning of bicycles among the local population.

On May 1st 2013, the AMECiclo entity (Metropolitan Association of Cyclists of Greater Recife) arises. On their website it presents itself as follows:

"The Metropolitan Association of Cyclists of Greater Recife area" - AMECiclo (2013) "has as its main axis of actions promoting the use of bicycles and democratization of public roads. In these terms, we intend to act politically through educational sporting and cultural activities in a single mosaic in which the priority is the awareness of the public nature of the urban fabric and the need to humanize it through peaceful coexistence between different modes of transport."

The AMECiclo and the Direitos Urbanos movements have been jointly outlining some dialog, presentation of ideas and integrated actions.

-
- 6 We adopt bike lane as an exclusive segregated space for cyclists and which features do not have a fixed separation. In Recife, they are isolated by mobile traffic cones.
 - 7 We adopt bike patch as an exclusive segregated space for cyclists and isolated steadily. This separation, in Recife, is basically made by concrete blocks and is located bordering the urban beaches of the south of the city.

Figure 2. Culture and Leisure Bike Lane, Recife – Brazil.

EXPLORING THE CONTENT OF POSTINGS

Looking at the records of the *Bicicletada Recife* group on Facebook, it was possible to establish an initial classification of posts, taking into consideration the arguments raised. The findings categories are reported below, though an analytical incursion into these various contributions to the *Bicicletada* website.

1. Posts that articulate and celebrate the construction of various networks about cycling in the city. The speech transcribed below illustrates the reasons that underlie the interests of so-called "pedal groups", whose objectives are considered distinct from those adopted by most participants of the *Bicicletada Recife*.

John: "about bias or pseudo-bias, I can speak for myself as an administrator of a night cycling group with more than one hundredth users. A large part of all the people who participate in pedal group is not interested in "wasting" their time protesting, arguing, seeking. Finally, they are there with the following interests: cycling, exercising, showing off, flirting, troll, etc., things like that, you know?"

The speech also records a specific conflict that is evident among the *Bicicletada Recife* participants: on the one hand, the interests of the cyclists who wish to hold a protest action, highlighting its political dimension and, second, the interests of those who seek, above all, the fun dimension.

2. Posts related to consumption associated with the practice of cycling. Several posts are related to sales and purchases of supplies and services. Some participants are looking for information about the acquisition of items associated with the practice of cycling, or about quality, advantages for safety, strength, reuse and customization of bikes.

Anna: "Why shopkeepers offer and sell expensive bikes and accessories to leisure bike lane users, who are not athletes?"

Mary: "About the shopkeepers that offer and sell expensive bikes and accessories to bike lane users who are not athletes. Well, many of these people think they are athletes. There are also people in a pedal group that ride once or twice

a week, who swear that they are athletes. Then, the shopkeeper takes advantage to make money and, honestly, I don't think it is wrong."

In this category, one can also observe the ideological perspectives of the participants, some of them conflicting. For example, the critical words related to the topic of consumption, which highlights the different interests between participants recognized as sportsmen and those who seek to cycle for fun, or think that they are professional cyclists, through the use of accessories and clothes.

The debate also highlights the efforts made by the alignment of these ideas in the group, or alternatively the search for dialogue among people interested in cycling, regardless of whether they want to be seen as social and political movements or not. This strategy ensures the possibility of building a shared patrimony of experiences and memories, despite the ideological differences.

The second speech expresses the view of some participants who recognize the traders as part of the collaborative movement. They recognize the collaboration of the world of trade and do not express prejudice against certain consumption practices, conceiving them as an important part in this field of practice.

3. Posts that criticize the initiatives related to the provision of services by municipal, state and private entities that provide bicycles and the urban infrastructure required for cycling. In the example below, still talking about "pedal groups," the author of the post points out:

John: "I do not remember writing that the "pedal" groups were the forerunners of the movement. Those who really make use of bikes expository and assiduously never represented anything to the governments, unfortunately, "(...)" and only count the number of bike paths and lanes in the outlying regions of the city. "

Through the analysis of this category of posting, we observed that participants seem to commune with the idea that it's necessary to push the State for effective actions to improve the urban infrastructure required for cycling. This goal presents itself as a common point in discourses that rest on different ideologies.

4. Posts that show self-criticism of the participants in relation to what would be a desirable social behavior in meetings. Participants of the *Bicicletada Recife* criticize the behavior of the other cyclists, exposing some practices that denounce a lack of civility in the coexistence of the group.

Amy: "Critical Mass could do more, if would show more ideal. You cannot make people believe your ideas doing what is done. In went out in the *Bicicletada*; a cyclist stopped a car... the driver asked him to move and the biker did not let him through. Then the driver drove the car against the cyclist. The car was dented and the cyclist started to kick the car. The driver was rescuing a woman who was sick. I saw! I was next to the car! Is that what we want to show?" "What impression did people go away with?"

The speech registers the participants' concern over how they are perceived by society as a result of their actions; namely, the desire for a positive image of cyclists' behavior, both internally in the group and to society at large. This reflection is consistent with the considerations of Halbwachs (1990), when the author examines the ties that bind the representations of the individual experience (substrate of the individual memory) with the collective memory.

"If these two memories are often interpenetrated; if the individual memory can confirm some of our individual mind records, rests on the collective memory, moving on it, becoming momentarily with it, it doesn't mean that it leaves its own way; and all that exterior source is gradually assimilated and incorporated into its substance. The collective memory, for the other side, involves the individual memories, but do not blend with it. It changes according to its own laws, and some individual memories sometimes penetrate it, changing the shape as they were replaced in other context that is not a personal conscience". (Halbwachs, 1990, p 54. Translated by the authors).

In the above passage, the author defines the two forms of memory that are built by people and the linkages between them. He highlights the preponderance of this second type in the constitution of broader social meanings, and as a repository with which it completes its own individual memory, that constantly appropriates and incorporates the collective memory. This construction allowed us to understand the concerns expressed in the transcript speech, related to the social representations of the group, substrate for the collective memory of the movement.

5. Posts related to (re) discovery of certain places and uses of the city. There are several postings of videos through which cyclists show emblematic places, highlighting the beauty and denouncing the evils of the city. Through these posts, cycling is constituted as a tool that enables to reveal facets of the city that are almost never displayed, providing the critical appropriation of these locations and information about them by the population, the extent to which the images are exposed to wider society through the website. In this case, it is clearly expected that individual actions contribute to the repository of collective memory, and, in turn, that repository of collective memory serves to prime basis for other individual memories.
6. Posts that highlight the dimension of the movement at local, national and international levels.

Dan: Join the Critical Mass / *Bicicletada* of January! Over 400 people have already confirmed. Get your bike (or any human-powered vehicle) and come to fight for a more humane city! (...) The "mass" is everyone, including you! Unlike many cycling "pedal" groups, a representative part of the people who participate in *Massa Crítica /Bicicletada* share the idea that we should take to the streets, using human-powered vehicles, fighting for respect, space, justice etc., since there is a pre-

dominating ideology that cities, especially the roads, were made for motorized modals. In this sense, Critical Mass/ Bicletada is a mix of protest, celebration and occupation, which takes place—anarchically—on the last Friday of each month.

Similarly, the exposure of remote images of the city contributes to potentiating its collective memory, registering the link of the group with national and international movements with similar objectives (in this case, the link with the Critical Mass movement) is also strategic as a inclusion of elements to this collective memory.

DISCUSSING THE SUBJECT

From the examination of selected posts that analyze the concept of the cycling movement, we observed more clearly: the amount of individual enjoyment among participants, their collective embeddedness at local level (political, vindicating) and also its connection with international movements with similar ideologies. This incursion has enabled us to discuss the process by which a common interest arises through the collective practice of cycling: the possibility of enjoying new locations of the city that were previously inaccessible, or with which we had no experience; the feeling that it is possible to act and intervene in the patterns of the urban environment; and the playful dimension, among others.

From the collected data, we can also infer that the context of cycling contributes to the production of a responsible perception of the city. This process is made possible both by the sharing of relationships promoted in the context of cycling events, as by the very capability of the mediation artifacts involved, especially the bicycle. The bicycle integrates the city's representations because of its relational dimension that sets in motion the prerogative of contributing to society's experiences. Its emblematic role of mobilizer sign in the social process follows this prerogative (Gell, 2011).

Much of the content available on posts refers to the claims of the conditions that allow cyclists, especially the bike lane users, the feeling of relative freedom to enjoy the city. We can say, following the suggestion of Halbwachs (1990) that the construction of emotional ties and the construction of a collective memory of urban space among this group are made possible through the emotional experiences of sharing relations in this context.

We note that there is a feedback between the fun sense of the enjoyment of cycling, the local political movement, claiming their own space for this practice, and also a larger political movement with international roots, motivated by a search for health, leisure, urban mobility, all associated with the possibility of getting to and from the city.

These aspects are highlighted in some dialogues, involving discussion about the political dimension of the Critical Mass group, in a continuous process of provocation and irony, on the one hand, and mediation and rationality, on the other.

George: Could someone explain to me what a “pedal” group is? I saw some comments here, but I not understand. It is a bus that takes people to a destination, and from there people go to their own way, to their own chosen places?

Harry: Bicletada Group means cicloactivism; and pedal groups are ciclocapitalism. They differ in their purposes and ideals.

Susan: Ready: spoke the voice of political liberalism! Indeed, lack of focus. When you buy your bike, it is already ciclocapitalism, isn't? Unless you stole a bike...

George: ... but Susan, I think he (Harry) compares someone who buys a bike because of his work and someone who buys the bike to ride. I think this concept doesn't help because it is very strong. I prefer ciclobusiness rather than ciclocapitalisms.

Analyzing the conceptualizations of *cicloactivism*, *ciclocapitalism* and *ciclobusiness* for these informants, it is possible to realize, as suggested by Halbwachs, the importance of individual memories, or of the various meanings attributed to cycling by these people, in the construction of a collective image for the urban space. These constructions would also fit into Halbwachs' concept of collective memory.

Some posts, in turn, try to refine the meaning of the bicycle, drawing attention, beyond the political dimension and the appropriation of the city, also to the recreational experience and familiarity involved with the use of this artifact:

Amy: Pedal group: is a group in which people with the same intention gather to ride. They can be contrary to what many want, but they do what each one wants. We are not obligated to protest about anything! And contrary to what many think, THEY HELP TO SPREAD WHAT A BIKE IS: A MEANS TO IMPROVE HEALTH, DO SPORT AND ENJOY LEISURE. And EVERY ONE GOES THEIR YOUR OWN WAY! I think pedal groups are cool, because they are organized and fun. Moreover, they teach beginners how to pedal and people how to behave in traffic. Nobody gets to ride to get hit. We live in Brazil and not in Holland! What is this? This idea of car bureaucracy or whatever they call it is in totally disagreement ... Do you want to change Brazil? Start with yourself, encourage someone to ride, teach him a pleasant way to respect the cyclists. THAT'S WHAT THEY TEACH. See the APS, a wonderful group! It brings together people of all ages, people who have a car and who respect cyclists. To oppose the reality is a waste of time. Violence begets violence and that is what we have. I am in favor of kindness.

It is worth highlighting the above speaker's description, when he points out that pedal groups, although they have no major political claims, are "organized and fun", and contribute to the affective experience of cycling itself, in the construction of social meanings.

Other speakers point out that, apart from the idiosyncrasies that affect the relationships among participants (individu-

ally), generating difficulties by different ideologies, there is a converging motivation, synthesized in the interest of improving the urban space:

Ted: There is so much to discuss, I think we should be more united and fight for the same cause, which is in favor of making improvements in the city for more spaces for bikes!

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

To understand the constructed memory of the *Bicicletada Recife* group on Facebook, it was necessary to seek a phenomenological point of view that makes it possible to approach the city as an artifact that provides the context for this construction.

The posts of the *Bicicletada Recife* group contribute to the empirical glimpse of what would be, following Halbwachs perspective, a process through which a group of individuals who, in the dynamics of their narratives (descriptions and conflicts), reproduce a macro-collective memory of international scope about the use and meaning of the bike. This memory is permeated by the defense of sustainable and humane cities, issues related to urban mobility, urban rights and everyday practices of leisure and health. The bike artifact integrates this phenomenon as an emblematic artifact that embodies, or integrates, the desire for action of those involved.

As the initial step of a broader research project, we believe that the work displayed in this article needs improvements and insights. The issue of collecting and processing the data is still a challenge, though we intend to continue to invest in methodological netnography models.

We assumed that the recovery of the memories related to experiences and emotions in cycling would help to reveal the meanings that the members of the *Bicicletada Recife* group attach to the bike and its use. Taking into consideration the methodological user-centered-design proposal aims, we can realize, pragmatically, that the approach of the collective memory may provide support for the design and redesign of some products, systems and services related to cycling. For this, we intend to consider the relationship of memory building with the construction of the meanings we attribute to artifacts, even if we do not use them directly.

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FROM: GOVERNMENT, TO: CITIZENS

- WRITING WITH CARE -

Miguel Gandour

Consultant at Gandour Consultores, Colombia

Economist from the Universidad de los Andes, Colombia

✉ mgandour@gandourconsultores.com

Carlos Ortiz

Consultant at Gandour Consultores, Colombia

Industrial Engineer from the Universidad de los Andes, Colombia

✉ cortiz@gandourconsultores.com

Diana Rocha

Consultant at Gandour Consultores, Colombia

Economist from the Universidad de los Andes, Colombia

✉ drocha@gandourconsultores.com

Cristina Mejía

Consultant at Gandour Consultores, Colombia

Lawyer from the Universidad de los Andes, Colombia

✉ cmejia@gandourconsultores.com

Marcela Angel

Consultant at Gandour Consultores, Colombia

Architect from the Universidad de los Andes, Colombia

✉ mangel@gandourconsultores.com

ABSTRACT

This paper presents an *Effective Communications Strategy* implemented by an agency of the Colombian Government that was based on the integration of insights from evidence-based policy design, design thinking, behavioral economics and plain language techniques. Effective communication creates an emotional connection that effectively communicates a message. It also encourage citizens to take action. The strategy encouraged citizens and businesses to present accurate reports and pay contributions to the Social Protection System. First, we describe how we integrated insights from different disciplines in order to design and implement an *Effective Communications Strategy*. We then show how we applied this integration into mass-mail letters and e-mails sent to employees in order to encourage them to act as first line auditors of their employers and to enforce their rights. As we advanced in the design thinking process the percentage of employees who opened and read the letters increased from 17 to 94%. This was a significant result, achieved before it was decided to implement the strategy on a larger scale. The paper represents an attempt to contribute to the way governments can design and implement effective communications by integrating and applying knowledge from different disciplines.

KEYWORDS: *Social Protection System, fiscal and financial sustainability, contributions, compliance, behavioral economics, design thinking, plain language, prototyping.*

INTRODUCTION

Social Protection Systems (SPS) are a set of guarantees provided by governments in order to make a positive difference to the lives of citizens. According to the International Labour Organization (ILO, 2012, 5), these guarantees are: *i*) access to essential health care; *ii*) basic income security, access to nutrition, education and care for children, *iii*) basic income security for citizens of active age who are unable to earn sufficient income (e.g. in case of sickness, unemployment, maternity and disability) and, *iv*) basic income security for the elderly (e.g. pensions). These guarantees “are an economic and social necessity for development and progress, and an important tool to prevent and reduce poverty, inequality and social exclusion and insecurity” (ILO, 2012, 31).

‘Financial and fiscal sustainability’ is one of the essential principles on which SPS rely to prevent and reduce poverty,

inequality, social exclusion and insecurity. This principle balances short- and long-term benefits with the cost of the System (ILO, 2012, 17).

In Colombia, the ‘financial and fiscal sustainability’ principle is undermined by the existence of high levels of evasion of the contributions that finance the SPS. Employers, employees and the self-employed are obliged to contribute to the System. However, a considerable number of people do not fully comply with their obligations. According to the UGPP (*Unidad de Gestión Pensional y Parafiscales*), the Colombian government agency responsible for promoting social security and payroll tax compliance, contributors evaded 26.8% of their obligations in 2012 (UGPP, 2013, 1). This percentage corresponds to approximately USD 7.3 billion per year. Such evasion levels have important social impacts such as economic insecurity, social exclusion and an unhealthy and unproductive workforce (ILO, 2012, 17).

The UGPP has been working to design and implement innovative strategies intended to reduce evasion and, therefore, guarantee financial and fiscal sustainability of an SPS that makes a difference in people's lives. Audits (the traditional way to enforce compliance) are not feasible if they are the only strategy implemented by a government. Due to the finite nature of resources, the UGPP could never reach all evaders by using audits, because they are expensive, and the number of evaders is high. Also, if audits are not implemented jointly with other strategies that aim to gain the trust of contributors and generate the perception that government is an ally that defends citizens' rights, they might encourage more evasion instead of reducing it (Swedish Tax Agency, 2005).

This paper aims to describe one such innovative strategy, which we call *Effective Communications*. As advisors to the UGPP in the design and implementation of this strategy, we integrated insights from evidence-based policy design, design thinking, behavioral economics and plain language techniques. The paper describes the integration process of these insights, and their expected effects on citizens' behavior.

We also present a specific application of this strategy, which consisted of 615,000 e-mails and letters sent to employees. In these communications the UGPP i) informed employees about the payments made by their employers on their behalf; ii) encouraged them to compare those payments with the deductions made by their employers from their salaries; and, iii) gave them instructions on how to act if there were discrepancies between these deductions and their employer contributions (if deductions were higher than payments this might mean that the employer was retaining a fraction of the salary they should have been contributing to the system). Before sending the letter en masse to 615,000 employees, we developed various prototypes, which evolved as we integrated knowledge drawn from design thinking and other approaches. With the first prototype we encouraged only 17% of employees to open and read the letters, whilst in the last version 94% of employees did so. This was an important result, achieved before deciding to carry out the mass mail-out.

The research presented in this paper is intended to contribute to the ways in which governments can formulate and implement strategies that effectively influence behavior. Although this is not necessarily a trend in developed countries, in developing countries such as Colombia, governments usually rely on 'traditional' knowledge (e.g. law, economics, etc.) to design and implement policies, generally turning to regulatory proposals in order to promote compliance. Governments can integrate design and other non-traditional approaches at any stage during the public development process, in order to produce effective strategies.

In particular, this work is a contribution to the way governments communicate with their citizens. In the case of the UGPP, this strategy is the first step in a new direction towards improving communication with contributors. It acknowledges the importance of using trans-disciplinary knowledge; it recalls the usefulness of testing policies on a small scale before applying them on a larger scale; it recognizes the power

of prototyping; and it uses plain language in order to communicate with citizens in a simple and transparent manner, without punitive intention. It is a new direction that requires governments to "write with care".

THE CHALLENGE: PROMOTING SOCIAL PROTECTION CONTRIBUTIONS COMPLIANCE THROUGH EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATIONS

Evasion is measured as the difference between potential contributions and actual contributions made to the SPS. In 2012 the UGPP estimated evasion of SPS contributions for the first time in Colombian history. This estimate was made on the basis of information from 60,000 individuals that were statistically representative of the population obliged to contribute to the SPS. The estimate indicated that in 2012 evasion amounted to 26.8%, corresponding to USD 7.3 billion. Of those USD 7.3 billion, USD 4.28 billion represented evasion in the pension system (59% of total evasion), and USD 2.61 billion evasion in the health care system (36% of total evasion) (the UGPP, 2013, 1-2).

The estimate also indicated that there were many people evading small amounts of money. Most individuals evaded on average between USD 25 and USD 75 per month. Consequently, traditional strategies such as desk audits and regulatory initiatives were not cost-effective, because they were very expensive compared to the potential resources that they might help recover. In response, we proposed alternative, cost-effective, strategies that might change people's behavior. Particularly, we came up with the *Effective Communications Strategy* that we present in this paper.

The purpose of this communication strategy was i) to motivate people to pay attention to what the UGPP had to say to them, ii) to provide information that mattered to people, and iii) to give clear instructions to people about how to start complying with their SPS obligations.

To accomplish that purpose we integrated tools from plain language techniques, behavioral economics, evidence-based policymaking and design thinking. Plain language was necessary to design a message according to the reader's point of view. Behavioral economics promoted a change in the behavior of readers, encouraging them to verify that the contributions made by their employers were filed accurately. Evidence-based policy provided the tools necessary for the design of the prototypes that would produce the scientific evidence necessary to validate the initiative. Design thinking was central to the iterative learning process developed with the use of prototypes and the human centered approach that allowed the team to assume the reader's position.

The communication channel

Along with staff from the UGPP we decided that the best way to communicate with people in order to influence their behavior and thus promote compliance, was by sending them

e-mails and/or letters. The UGPP needed to provide confidential information to each individual, so massive generic communications (e.g. advertisements) were not useful. Also, the UGPP had access to individuals' home and e-mail addresses, which facilitated the use of letters and e-mail. Finally, e-mails and letters were also more cost-effective than desk audits and the UGPP had experience in their use.

Letters and e-mails were also an alternative to traditional regulation, which is usually supported by the publication of laws or other legal documents. The Organization for Cooperation and Development (OECD) an intergovernmental organization that gathers best practices in public policy around the world, has stated that e-mails and/or letters are a useful alternative to regulation when governments seek to change behavior "through the provision of greater information or changing the distribution of information. That is, [advancing] information which may be available to some businesses and consumers and not to others... The objective may be to provide information that is either too difficult for consumers to collect themselves or would be too costly to gather" (OECD, 2012, 51).

The use of multiple tools for designing and testing communications

Besides selecting the communication channel, we also had to be able to communicate a message effectively. It is well documented that governments have difficulty in communicating in a simple and easily understood manner (Federal Plain Language Guidelines, 2011). We used plain language techniques and insights from behavioral economics to overcome this difficulty and to induce people to act according to the purpose of the messages.

Plain language (Sunstein, 2011, 1) encourages greater transparency and accountability on the part of governments urging them to communicate using clear and concise messages written with the reader in mind (Plain English Campaign). Implementing plain language in government communications can "improve public understanding, save money and increase efficiency, reduce the need for the public to seek clarification from agency staff, improve public understanding of agency requirements, reduce resources spent on enforcement and reduce the number of errors that are made and thus the amount of time and effort that the agency and the public need to devote to correcting errors" (Sunstein, 2011, 2). According to the Australian Government, the principles of plain language are: *i*) choose the straightforward option, *ii*) keep sentences short, *iii*) use an active voice, *iv*) use you and we, *v*) give instructions directly, *vi*) choose words appropriate for the readers, *vii*) avoid nominalizations, and *viii*) use lists (Government of South Australia).

For example, the Internal Revenue Service (the US tax agency) has started to transform its communications using plain language techniques. The director of the IRS identified the need to transform the organization's communications when she received a letter about her tax return and had to read it five

times before she understood what it was saying (Center for American Progress, 2011). The project's results were the redesign of "85 of the most commonly sent letters, accounting for 50 percent of the correspondence volume. New notices were based on nine prototypes, each of which had been tested for user-friendliness by a sample of 400 representative taxpayers" (Center for American Progress, 2011).

Behavioral economics insights are useful for evaluating empirically how people react to different messages, which may vary in form and content, and for understanding the way people react to those messages. For example, the Behavioral Insights Team (BIT) in the United Kingdom has carried out several experiments within the process of designing effective communications to reduce fraud, error and debt, based on seven lessons from behavioral economics. These lessons are: 1) make it easy (e.g. produce easy to follow instructions), 2) highlight key messages, 3) use personal language, 4) prompt honesty and key moments, 5) tell people what others are doing, 6) reward desired behavior, and 7) highlight the risk and impact of dishonesty (Behavioral Insights Team, 2012, 4). One particular experiment conducted by the BIT was related to the use of color in letters. In this experiment the BIT showed how highlighting a section of the message with bright red or blue makes it more likely to be believed than using green or yellow (Behavioral Insights Team, 2012, 10). The experiments conducted by the BIT also concluded that people commonly focus on information given at the beginning of letters.

We decided to test the impact of the initiative and make the corresponding adjustments using one of the central tools of evidence-based policy and design thinking: prototyping. Prototypes allow governments to test, evaluate and adjust initiatives before they are implemented on a larger scale (Nesta, 2011). Prototyping in government *i*) provides an opportunity to test new ideas without the pressure of obtaining immediate positive results, *ii*) facilitates the participation of a wide range of actors that are interested in the testing occurring; *iii*) allows experimentation over short time periods and, *iv*) enables an iterative learning environment (Nesta & ThinkPublic, 4). Prototyping is also useful to test the cost-effectiveness of a policy in terms of fulfilling its objectives and it shows others how to implement a successful public policy (Ettelt *et al.*, 2013).

Besides prototypes, we used three additional elements of design thinking: *i*) designing within the practical constraints of sending a large number of communications, *ii*) creating an interdisciplinary team, and *iii*) implementing a human centered perspective with input from readers. For the first element, we identified the feasibility, viability and desirability of the initiative, taking into account the approach developed by the design consultancy IDEO that "the first stage of the design process is often about discovering which constraints are important and establishing a framework for evaluating them" (Brown, 2009). For the second element, we formed an interdisciplinary team of lawyers, engineers, economists, architects and designers to create collective ownership of ideas. For the third element, we used a human-centered approach

to increase the likelihood of developing a breakthrough idea from the standpoint of the reader (Brown, 2009). To do this, we monitored readers' responses to every prototype through surveys. We also incorporated design thinking in the iterative use of prototyping. We validated the strategy through two prototypes that allowed us to "avoid costly mistakes such as becoming too complex too early and sticking with a weak idea for too long" (Brown, 2009).

THE APPLICATION: ONE PAGE LETTER

All the elements described in the last section were integrated and applied to the design of a letter that effectively alerted employees about the payments that their employers made to the SPS on their behalf. We needed to empower the employees through letters and e-mails so they could act as auditors of their employers. Our goal was to expose the behavior of dishonest employers by reducing the information asymmetries that existed between employers and employees regarding the accurate payment of the social security contributions, so that they could enforce their rights.

In the e-mails or physical letters sent to the homes of employees, we provided information about the taxable income declared by the employer on behalf of the employee. The communication also gave information about the total amount of contributions made by the employer to the pension and healthcare systems and the deductions that the employer should have made in order to contribute the correct amount. Through these communications the UGPP invited employees to contrast the information they received with the payroll vouchers that their employers gave them and to follow several steps if there was a difference.

To test the effectiveness of the communication we developed one field experiment using two prototypes. We sent over 1,492 letters in the experimentation phase and 615,000 letters during the large-scale implementation phase (mass mail-out).

The process was divided into three phases: *i*) experiment planning, *ii*) experiment implementation including two small-scale prototypes and *iii*) mass mail-outs of the letter and e-mails to 615,000 employees.

Phase 1: Planning the Experiment

The experiment-planning phase consisted of *i*) the identification of the profiles of the employees to whom the communication (by letter and e-mail) would be sent and *ii*) the first draft of the communication.

Identification of the profiles

The selection of the people who would receive the communication was based on the identification of employers who might pay less than they were obliged to (inaccurate contributions). Ideally we should have identified those who were

also hiding information from their employees, but this was not possible to determine because only employers have access to this information.

To identify employers who potentially provide incorrect information the team worked with the same data used in the 2012 estimate of evasion. We carried out a statistical analysis to understand the factors that increase the probability of being an employee whose employer is making inaccurate contributions. Through this analysis we found that there is a 45% probability or higher that inaccurate contributions will have been made if employees: *i*) earned USD 750 or more on a monthly basis; *ii*) worked in real estate activities, in organizations which provide health services or in the retail trade; *iii*) worked in firms with 10 or more employees and, *iv*) did not live in the Atlantic (Caribbean) Region. So, the communications were targeted at employees with these characteristics

One additional condition was considered in the particular case of the e-mails: employees had to be 40 years old or younger. This was based on the findings of five different studies by the Colombian Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications regarding the relationship between citizen demographics and e-mail use (Coneus, K. Y Schleife, K., 2010; MinTic, 2010; MinTic et al., 2010; MinTic et al., 2012; DANE, 2013).

First Draft: Content proposal

The first draft of the communication was designed using elements of plain language and the results of investigations by the BIT. For example, we wrote the communication in the first person in order to generate empathy with the employee. We also included easy-to-follow instructions on how to verify the taxable income reported by employers.

The communication was intended to persuade employees to check if the Taxable Income specified in the letter was the same as that reported on the payroll vouchers they received from their employers (see *Figure 1*).

We then reviewed this communication and identified a number of difficulties: *i*) it did not explain which document the recipient should compare the information to, *ii*) the information was difficult to understand because it attached the entire contributions report, *iii*) the letter did not differentiate total Taxable Income from the deductions from the employee's wage (information that is easy to access since it is included on the payroll voucher) and *iv*) the communication had no layout design.

Taking these aspects into account the content was adapted (see *Figures 2 and 3*). The amended communication did not include the entire contributions report and only specified the relevant information we wanted to validate: Taxable Income, total contributions made by the employer to the pension and healthcare systems, and the deduction that the employer should have made according to the reported taxable income and the contributions made to pensions and healthcare systems.

Now that we knew that the language was easy to understand the prototype was ready to be sent to the first 493 employees.

Figure 1. First Draft

Figure 2. First Prototype (front)

Figure 3. First Prototype (back)

Phase 2: Experiment implementation and prototypes

It was decided to implement the project using an experimental phase, because we wanted to engage in an iterative learning process. We varied the content and layouts and adapted the communication based on the feedback received from employees.

The experimentation phase was a safe context in which to implement a design-driven approach as part of a government initiative.

The first prototype

The pilot consisted of the physical mailing of the first prototype of the letter to 493 employees, selected using the criteria chosen during the planning phase. To validate the impact of the pilot we prepared a survey, in which we asked employees if they had: i) read the letter, ii) understood the message and, iii) followed the instructions.

The UGPP selected 50 employees randomly to participate in the survey. Of those 50 employees that were selected, only 12 responded, of whom only two said that they opened the letter/read the e-mail. This translates into an effectiveness of only 17% in persuading people to read the letter.

This finding made us realize that we needed to rethink the prototype. If we wanted the message to reach our target, we needed to appeal to people's emotions in order to attract their attention and ensure they opened the letter.

The redesign

During the development of the design process we realized we needed a change our perspective, so we decided to implement an inter-disciplinary approach championed by design thinking. We added a practising architect and a graphic designer to our team of economists, engineers and lawyers.

We started the redesign by formulating fundamental questions about the concept of the letter: What is a letter? Why do people read letters? How could we get people to read our letter? How could we generate curiosity and make it attractive to readers? Who were our readers? Why should they read the message? What is the problem? What should our readers do to solve the problem? How might they do this? When should they do it? Why is the issue important?

The first insight came from the definition of a letter. A letter is a communication that one person sends to another to communicate a message. We learned that we needed to highlight the name of the employee we were directing the letter to, and identity of the sender using the UGPP logo. We did not know if the logo would have an effect, since only 0.1% of the population in Colombia had heard of the UGPP, so we decided to include the logo of the Ministry of Finance and Public Credit too. We were not going to follow the standard of an official communication from a government agency, but we needed to be careful differentiating the letter from an advertisement.

The second insight came from understanding the differences between an open letter and a closed communication. Each of these has different objectives and we needed to prioritize and classify the information accordingly. The outside of the letter needed to generate curiosity and tell the person why the communication was important to them, and the inside should contain the confidential information, instructions and also motivate the employee to follow them.

The third insight came from understanding the deep structure of the content, allowing us to simplify and divide it into different sections. We decided the communication was going to be sent with a “z” fold as a self-enveloped letter. This meant that the content had to be divided into six sections.

Figure 4. Redesign draft

A priority in the redesign of the letter was to understand the needs and desires of the people who were going to receive it. The main elements that were changed to achieve a higher impact were *i*) the content, colors and style of the cover and back of the letter, *ii*) the new layout of the content including elements from infographics, and *iii*) simpler text and instructions (see Figure 4).

The cover of the letter was designed to consist of a question in bold white letters on a red background. We insisted on the importance that the cover should be red to increase the likelihood of attracting attention. The question “(Name of the employee), do you know if (name of the company), paid your social security accurately?” was an instrument to generate curiosity, talking directly to the employee. The back of the letter addressed why it was important, informing the employee of the 3 main risks if their employer was not paying correctly. With all these elements we intended to persuade people to open the letter rather than consider it junk mail (see Figure 5).

The extensive paragraphs were transformed into smaller sections with infographics that easily communicated the message. This allowed us to guide the recipient rapidly through the sections in which the most important information was displayed.

The text was simplified and titles were added to each section in the form of questions to enforce the active voice of the UGPP. The instructions were enumerated and included easy-to-follow steps. This structure was designed to motivate the employees to follow the steps and verify if their employers had paid the correct contributions. The contact information of the UGPP was highlighted to make it easier to respond to additional questions. Particular fonts - family and size - were chosen to give hierarchy to the messages.

The communications included information on the deductions the employer should have made, the total contributions to the healthcare and pension systems, and the Taxable Income reported by the employer for a specific month. This information was confidential and was placed in the sections of the letter that were only visible when it was opened. The letter also highlighted the benefits of making accurate contributions (see Figures 6 and 7).

Figure 5. Outside of the letter

Figure 6. Second Prototype B&W (front)

Figure 7. Second Prototype B&W (back)

Second Prototype

The second prototype was sent to 999 employees. It was sent in black and white because we had budget restrictions that meant we could not hire a third party capable of color printing in time to meet the mailing deadline.

This prototype was validated in a different way. Among the 999 employees, the team knew 15 recipients personally. They had different backgrounds and they did not know in advance that they were going to receive the communication. This allowed us to document their reactions in more detail. The trade-off this implied was that these 15 employees were not randomly chosen (compared to the employees selected for testing the first prototype), but we needed more detailed feedback regarding the communications and decided to proceed with this option.

Based on the answers given by the 15 employees, we concluded that this second prototype improved effectiveness: people opened and read the letter. Of the 15 employees, 14 opened the letter. This corresponds to 94% effectiveness, which is almost 6 times the effectiveness of the original prototype, though we should be careful with this comparison for the reasons explained in the last paragraph. Despite the success of this prototype, all of our 15 acquaintances agreed that the letters would have had greater impact if they had been printed in color.

Figure 8. Second Prototype (front)

Figure 9. Second Prototype (back)

Figure 10. E-mail version

Phase 3: Mass mail-out

Once the team had validated the initiative using the two prototypes, the director of the UGPP had enough evidence to make the decision to carry out a mass mail-out of the final version of the letter. The process of sending the communication was divided into two phases: i) modifying the document according to the parameters and formats required by the supplier and ii) adapting and planning the e-mail version of the communication. The UGPP sent 615,000 letters, which incorporated all the lessons learned during the experimental phases.

CONCLUSIONS

The mass mail-out of 615,000 letters to different employees in Colombia was the first large-scale application of the Effective Communications Strategy. For the UGPP, this was a first attempt to understand employees' attitudes towards government communications, inform them about their rights within the SPS and encourage them to act as first line auditors of their employers. It was the first step in the process of "writing with care".

This first mass mail-out took into account the learning from the experimental phases, carried out on a small scale. In particular, it included the elements that had been designed to persuade people to open and read a letter. The results of the experimental phases were straightforward regarding the power of integrating different approaches, in particular de-

sign thinking. With the first prototype only 17% of employees to open and read the letter, while with the second prototype, which included more design-thinking elements, the percentage increased to 94%.

A final step for reviewing the social impact of the letters sent by the UGPP would be to evidence changes in the compliance of contributions of employers whose employees had received a letter. A first step of the mass-mail project was to make the letter attractive in order to increase the likelihood it would be opened and read. Next, we will need to evaluate if there has been a measureable social change in terms of higher compliance. Since the letters were sent out in mid-December 2013, we still have some time to observe the reactions of employees and their employers. In some cases we expect nothing to happen, while in others we would expect a reduction in non-compliance. The measurement of the impact was due to be carried out by the UGPP during the first semester of 2014.

The UGPP, or any other government agency, can apply the Effective Communications Strategy to different types of communications. Once public agencies have learnt to integrate insights from many disciplines, as the UGPP did, (using-evidence based public design, design thinking, plain language techniques, etc.), they will be able to carry out any number of communications actions intended to change people's behavior. A list of challenges faced by government agencies would be a sufficient starting point for innovating in the way public sector communicates.

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TROCA.CC: AN ENABLING PLATFORM FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL INNOVATION IN CALI, COLOMBIA

Javier Aguirre Ramos
✉ jaaguirre@icesi.edu.co

ABSTRACT

This paper provides insights into the development and results of a piece of academic research, which was based around the possibility of promoting social innovation in the city of Cali, Colombia, principally developed by “Creative Collectives” based in the city. The article is organized according to four theoretical pillars: Creative Communities, Collaborative Services, Social Innovation and Alternative Economic Models in order to examine the sustainability of these collectives. The results demonstrate that a platform established to promote processes of barter between members of the creative community for different elements might help sustain the work of collectives and, specifically, the origins of a development process that resulted in the creation of Troca.cc (The Creative Barter Collective).

KEYWORDS: *Social Innovation, Enabling Platforms, Collaborative Economies, Creative Communities, Barter.*

INTRODUCTION

In the City of Cali there are numerous creative collectives, most of which are community-based and whose activities focus on alternative means of communication. These collectives have developed different and interesting ways of combating social problems in the environments where they operate. Their work is primarily voluntary and is not motivated by profit. Nevertheless, some have managed to stay active for over 12 years. The principal motivation of this study was to understand how these collectives have managed to ensure sustainability against all economic odds.

Globalization tends to standardize cultural differences, politics and ideologies (Gumucio, 2003). Alternative means of communication, which emerge from the primary unit of cultural development, represent a clear line of defense against this standardization. Furthermore, these collectives tend to reject traditional economic models (Aguilera, 2011); they should therefore be supported. That being said, this support does not need to be strictly monetary, as their need for resources goes beyond the merely financial.

A theoretical review, and interviews conducted with the Collectives themselves determined that collaboration is a key

factor in their day-to-day existence. As such, this research was carried out in the hope of helping this collaboration grow and encouraging more people to become involved in an organized manner so as to develop a platform that would favor favour the sustainability of their organizations.

Theoretical Research

The theoretical basis of this research is four-fold, focusing on Creative Communities, Collaborative Services, Social Innovation and Alternative Economic Models. The following section explains the importance of these concepts to the research.

Creative Communities

Meroni (2007, quoted in Manzini, 2008), says the following about Creative Communities:

“They’re groups of people that cooperatively invent and manage better innovative solutions for new ways of living. This is done by recombining what already exists, without expecting a general change in the current system (economy, institutions and great infrastructures)”

That being said, it is important to note that Creative Communities are more than just groups of people that invent things.

They are living organisms that thrive on creativity and on the desire to face up to the social issues that surround them. The solutions that they create are mostly driven by the community itself, and they are designed as explicit responses to problems that directly affect the community.

Following this line of thinking, this research defines Creative Communities as groups of innovative people who generate solutions to specific problems, through collaborative work and the exchange of knowledge, both between members of the community itself and with other communities.

Collaborative Services

A Collaborative Service seeks to create something, be it physical or just knowledge, through large-scale collaboration between differently-minded individuals. Examples of this are Wikipedia and Linux, which are both open source and community driven (Tapscott, Williams, 2008). Collaborative Services usually tend to re-interpret technologies, which is basically, as Manzini (2008) states, the reshaping of existing services and technologies into something that derive their power from people and not from money. In this way, even though most technology tends to be market driven, it can usually be tweaked to serve other functions, such as collaboration.

For this research, perhaps the most important concept concerning Collaborative Services is the Enabling Platform - a kind of Collaborative Service that seeks to simplify the process of collaboration and, as such, augment its visibility and the likelihood that an individual will want to take an active part in a collaborative process. Enabling Platforms need to be accessible in different ways, and not be too time consuming, so that they are attractive to the community (Manzini, 2008).

Social Innovation

Social Innovation is a concept that seeks to exalt innovations that occur in a social context. These innovations usually appear as answers to different conditions of exclusion and abandonment suffered by some communities.

According to Howaldt and Schwarz (2010, quoted in Aguirre, 2011, p. 56), a Social Innovation implies:

“A new configuration of social practices, in a specific context, promoted by certain actors with the main objective of satisfying specific needs and solving specific problems. An innovation is, then, social, when it is known and accepted throughout a community, without any intention of profit”

Mulgan et al. (2006) argue that “Social Innovations must seek to change the balance of power, this means giving more control and power over their own existence to those who are relatively unprotected, thus advancing in basic social and justice questions”

For this research, Social Innovation will be understood as a novel solution, not motivated by profit, which seeks to re-

solve a specific problem and reduce the social breach in a determined context.

Alternative Economic Models

We live in a capitalistic world. As such, any kind of Alternative Economic Model must be different to capitalism. The important thing here is to not get caught up in the idea that it must be in its essence anti-capitalist - it just needs to think some things though in a different manner. Collaborative Economies provide an example of this.

The main asset in a Collaborative Economy is its members, who usually assume the role of collaborators. In many communities, productive activities are voluntary and receive no monetary recompense. That said, this doesn't mean that these activities are based on philanthropy. The members of these economies receive different benefits in exchange for their work. On the one hand, people who work in collaboration with others mainly do so because they love it. Also, taking part in big projects like these brings with it experience, visibility and connections, alongside personal growth and new knowledge (Tapscott, Williams, 2008).

Manzini (2008) says that one of the pre-existing conditions of these economies is that there must be a high degree of interdisciplinary connectivity between members of the community. This should be based on two key elements: knowledge and collaboration. That being said, it doesn't mean that knowledge markets are sites where ideas are exchanged through monetary transactions. They operate more like the Library of Alexandria, in which knowledge is built through the distribution and diffusion of existing knowledge. The product is knowledge, but it's not sold: it is shared in order to develop new knowledge in mind.

Taking into account the approach of the different authors referred to above, the possibility was raised of applying the skills of Interactive Media Design¹ practitioners to find sustainable alternatives for community cultural organizations in Cali. The brief involved designing an enabling technology platform based on the principles of the collaborative economy.

METHODOLOGY

Two methods were employed to carry out this project: the analysis of existing platforms and a focus group survey.

Analysis of existing platforms

At this stage it was decided to work with six technology platforms that support the funding of mass economic and non-economic development projects. To evaluate these plat-

¹ Interactive Media Design is a professional training program of the Icesi University in Cali, Colombia, which is especially interested in how design can exploit the potential of digital media from interaction design. http://www.icesi.edu.co/disenio_medios_interactivos/

forms, a matrix analysis using the following eight criteria was designed: Creating Community, Chance of support from the Community, Using media for dissemination and communication, Creation and manipulation of content, Type(s) of projects supported, Method of raising resources, Type of support provided by the platform and Returns made by projects to the community. The platforms analyzed were the following: Kickstarter², TakingItGlobal³, The Young Foundation⁴, Kiva⁵, Donación⁶ y Ciudadanos Activos⁷.

Focus group survey

Data collection involved qualitative research using a targeted survey to obtain relevant information from a range of community cultural organizations in Cali.

To code and analyze the surveys, a matrix analysis of the information obtained was carried out. The categories of analysis were:

- Identification: external evaluation of the collective;
- Project: internal collective approach to the initiative;
- Collaboration: determining the willingness of the collective to collaborate with others;
- Network: relationships with other groups and / or institutions;
- Financing: resources for achieving economic sustainability.

Five groups were surveyed, all of which are involved in creating alternative communication mechanisms in different areas. The following community organizations were analyzed: A Ritmo de Ladera, Cine pa'l Barrio, Satelite Sursystem, Femenas Festivas y La Direkta.

Data analysis

The most relevant results obtained from the analysis of the collected data were the following:

Analysis of existing platforms

- Grant-based platforms are always looking to establish engagement between recipients of funding and donors, creating small communities for each project.
- The most frequently-used media are the social networks Facebook and Twitter.
- Platforms with a stronger interest in creating a united community allow greater access to tools for creating and manipulating content.

Focus group survey

- The collectives surveyed seek to generate reflection in the communities where they operate, by providing information on social problems.

2 www.kickstarter.com

3 www.tigweb.org

4 www.youngfoundation.org

5 www.kiva.org

6 www.donaccion.org

7 www.ciudadanosactivos.com

- Lack of financial resources force the members of the different groups to meet their economic needs by other means, such as working in activities that are unrelated to the work of the collective.
- All groups surveyed make use of at least one social networking site as a tool for dissemination. They also use communication technologies as a means of making complaints and demands.
- Collaboration is an important asset, used to exchange knowledge and capital used in the construction of joint projects.
- All groups use free distribution licenses for the projects they use.
- The main sources of finance are volunteering and participation in various funding calls.

Determinants of Design

From the results obtained in the analysis of existing platforms and the focus group survey, the following design determinants for the development of the proposal were developed. The analysis determined that the most important aspects of the technology platform should:

- Enable collaboration and communication between groups and between them and the community.
- Permit users and communities to create and manipulate content.
- Allow groups to create projects, seeking the support of other groups and the community.
- Allow the creation of joint projects.
- Provide the ability to donate collective projects to the community.

Metaphor

Taking into account the theoretical works reviewed during the preparation of this paper and the interviews with different collectives, the following things became clear:

- Enabling platforms that seek to help the collectives are not motivated by money.
- Collectives are willing to collaborate with others.
- Most resources come from voluntary work and loans.
- They are familiar with the internet and social networking, using them to promote their activities.

Taking this analysis into account, it was a simple process to brainstorm practical and pragmatic proposals: to develop a web platform that emulates a social network and promotes collaboration between its members in the form of barter. With this concept, it was possible to encourage cooperation between groups through the internet, while taking money out of the equation.

The main metaphor employed in this design proposition is barter. Not only does this encapsulate the whole concept of the platform, but it provides us with the principal method

of interaction as well. Barter is not an activity that can be carried out mainly in the digital world. As such, it must be linked to something more material; these material elements are the second part of the metaphor, and consist of tradable elements. Three principal kinds of elements can be traded: Knowledge, Objects and Spaces. These categories are derived from the most commonly identified need of the collectives and reflect the areas on which they have collaborated most often in the past.

Next, things must exist that these collectives need and that they are willing to trade. In this paper these are known as “Needs”, (in opposition to “Wants” so that the categories don’t reflect the marketplace) and “Haves”. These elements must be associated with something other than the user. As the platform is intended to help these collectives with their activities, it made the most sense that users should be involved in concrete projects, which in turn would have “Needs” and “Haves”. In this way, the barter process initiates with a project, and not just with a user, promoting the creation of such projects in order to use the platform’s capabilities fully.

Finally, during interviews it was stated that a web platform that involves exchange usually brings up trust issues. As such, the platform should be able to provide users with an adequate way of deciding whether they can trust each other or not. With that in mind, trust is represented by two measurable variables, both community controlled, which are:

- Commendations: users can be commended by other users.
- Barter Reviews: both parties should review every aspect of the barter process once it has ended. This review consists both of a numerical value and a text review, which are made public through a user’s profile to everybody in the community.

The Digital Bartering Process

Once a user has created an account on the website, he/she needs to follow certain steps in order to engage in a successful bartering process. This process is quite open and user-defined, because that is how the collectives prefer it. The steps that a user has to follow for an effective bartering transaction are as follows:

- *Create some Haves*: users must always have things they’re willing to exchange before they can ask for something they Need. Otherwise, the barter metaphor would be completely void.
- *Create a Project*: the platform is project oriented. This means that everything should start, and end, with a project. It is not intended to be a marketplace based on barter, so the creation of projects is an indispensable process. This includes defining the Needs of the project, and adding the user’s Haves to it.
- *Find an adequate bartering partner*: this includes defining if the other user is trustworthy or not, by means of the variables mentioned above (reviews and commendations). It also involves the existence of a positive combi-

nation of Needs and Haves between the two users, to ensure the process is mutually satisfactory.

- *Define the terms of the barter*: both users have a chance to communicate with each other in order to define important terms in the barter, such as timeframes, duration of the barter in the case of a lease, location of the other user and possible meeting places, etc. The adequate definition of these elements is almost mandatory if an effective barter is to take place.
- *Barter*: the actual bartering process. This is usually done outside the digital world, so the platform exerts no control.
- *Finish the barter and review the process*: both users must mark the bartering process as finished, and then proceed to review the other user.

Users

The platform has three types of users:

- *Anonymous Users*: these may browse and view content. Their role in the ecosystem of the platform is to support project visibility.
- *Registered Users without projects*: these have access to the entire platform. They can search, see and comment on content such as news and can propose trades if they have registered some “Haves” on the platform
- *Registered Users with projects*: as with the above users, these can also register “Needs” in the project. They form the engine room of the community, since the projects are the focus of the interactions between developers and the site of real collaboration.

Architecture

The information architecture designed for the project is presented in Figure 1.

Technical Development

In the technical development of the platform the following tools were used and the following requirements taken into account:

Software

- Netbeans, one of several available free and open environment that allows development in Java programming language.
- JavaServer Faces (JSF) tool for creating user interfaces for web applications.

Customer requirements:

- Modern Browser that allows the correct display of the platform (Chrome, Opera, Firefox, Safari, Internet Explorer 9 +)
- HTML5
- Javascript
- CSS3

Figure 1: Platform Architecture

Other requirements

- Hosting must be on a dedicated server that hosts the database and application, with a minimum 6 GB of RAM, at least 500 GB of free memory, ports 3306, 8080, 8090, 4848, 8091 and 8191, enabled Intel Xeon 5130@2.00GHz processor and remote access to the server

Usability Testing

Methodology: Using printed wireframes to create a paper prototype, four users were asked to perform certain actions, using their finger as the mouse. The number of errors committed before the action was carried out was noted. Users were also interviewed about how they viewed the process.

User tests

Methodology: During the process of development and programming of the website, four iterations of user testing were performed, as a closed beta test with five users each. Tests focused on the overall usability of the site and the proper functioning of processes.

RESULTS

This research explored ways of increasing the sustainability of community cultural organizations in the city of Cali. We found that these organizations generally sustained their activities by relying on volunteer work, sharing, and accessing finance from government and other sources. The groups expressed the need for free, self-managed tools to ensure harmony with their ideological stance and their organizational guidelines and practices. The proposal involved the design of a technology platform based on a collaborative economy that

would promote the exchange of the spaces, objects, knowledge and assets that sustain these organizations. Although the platform does not directly involve economic exchanges, these can be managed through the platform. One of the main assets of the platform is trust, which constitutes the real heart of barter. The platform was designed and developed using free software, so administration and management must be undertaken by members of the community. The platform is not intended to act as yet another social network, which is why social networking (Facebook and Twitter) functions are associated with it.

Although the platform is in a functional Beta version, the groups have participated in the design, and it is expected that they will also take part in the use and consolidation of the platform as a tool that contributes to the sustainability of community cultural organizations in Cali.

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MAKING, EMOTION AND THE DRIVE TO RE-SHORE UK GARMENT MANUFACTURING

Douglas Atkinson
 London College of Fashion
 University of the Arts London
 ✉ datkinson@fashion.arts.ac.uk

ABSTRACT

Research suggests that the act of making with one's hands may be linked to emotional well-being. Yet fashion businesses seeking to return production to the UK are struggling to recruit the necessary skilled manufacturing workers. Given the estimated cost of depression to the UK economy and the sustainability benefits of returning local production it seems that there is potential for massive social benefit could such a workforce be mobilized. This position paper proposes novel design challenges and research questions for further exploration. Application of design methods and critical or speculative design to these challenges could help to raise social awareness of garment manufacture and increase the emotional wellbeing of manufacturing workers, while maintaining rates of production which would make re-shoring (returning to on-shore manufacturing in the UK) economically viable.

KEYWORDS: *making; depression; wellbeing; localism; social change.*

INTRODUCTION

After attending the 1964 World's Fair, scientist and author Isaac Asimov made several predictions of society fifty years in the future in 2014. Most notably he stated:

..."mankind will suffer badly from the disease of boredom... This will have serious mental, emotional and sociological consequences, and I dare say that psychiatry will be far and away the most important medical specialty in 2014. The lucky few who can be involved in creative work of any sort will be the true elite of mankind...

Indeed, the most somber speculation I can make about A.D. 2014 is that in a society of enforced leisure, the most glorious single word in the vocabulary will have become work!" (Asimov, 1964)

While we may not recognise a world of 'enforced leisure' much of this quote rings true. In Westernised, knowledge-based, service economies the majority of occupations are now computer mediated, with no tangible output from our labours. Asimov's 'disease of boredom' may in fact be described as depression by modern psychiatry. In Westernised societies rates of depression are significantly higher than in subsistence and manufacturing based economies and it has been argued that the act of exertion to fulfill basic human needs, particularly making with your hands, triggers the effort based reward mechanisms in the brain (Lambert, 2006).

This paper specifically focuses on the UK garment industry, which over the past three decades has off-shored most of its manufacturing to countries with lower labour costs, notably East Asia and Turkey. There has recently been growing interest in returning low volume, high value garment production to the UK, however due to the years of decline there is a significant skills and labour gap in highly trained machinists for garment production (CFE, 2009). This is particularly important for luxury fashion, where quality craftsmanship and a 'Made in the UK' label are key to brand identity and the uniqueness of the business model (Frontier Economics, 2012).

LITERATURE AND DISCUSSION

Garment Making and Wellbeing

In Art Therapy and Occupational Health, making textile-based craft items has been shown to provide emotional benefits, particularly in terms of grounding and coping mechanisms (Collier, 2011). Evidence also suggests that engagement with textile making in mid to late life may confer decreased risk of cognitive impairment due to aging (Schofield-Tomschin & Littrell, 2001). Riley (2011) and other Researchers exploring Occupational Health and Art Therapy (Collier, 2011; Reynolds, 2000; Riley, Corkhill & Morris 2013) draw conclusions based on the idea of the textile maker producing works which they have personally planned and executed, often more akin to

textile art than the manufacture of designed products. This presents researchers with an opportunity to explore different populations and whether industrial garment making can confer similar benefits. Prior studies often focus exclusively on women who already engage in craft activities. Peruzza & Kinsella (2010) note that none of the papers in their literature review of creative arts and making practices in occupational therapy focused on men. Study participants were overwhelmingly white, wealthy and generally middle aged or older. Therefore, such studies fail to challenge traditional stereotypes and explore the wider therapeutic benefits of textile making activities to society as a whole.

Asimov's prediction of a creative elite can be recognized in 2014, with the emergence of the 'Creative Class' (Florida, 2002). However, Florida's construction of the Creative Class still forms an elite removed from manufacture and whose value lies in ideas rather than execution. Such attitudes are seemingly endemic within westernized societies. Sadly, employed makers (as distinct from those engaging in making for leisure, studied by Collier, 2011, Reynolds, 2000, Riley 2011 and Riley, Corkhill & Morris 2013) are not the working elite Asimov (1964) predicted, they are still undervalued and as such fewer and fewer people enter skilled manufacturing professions. Skills are being lost the world over as more countries aspire to move away from a manufacturing based economy. This is evidently unsustainable, particularly with labour costs equalizing around the globe. While many initiatives are underway to return manufacturing to service and knowledge based economies, there are often insufficient remaining workers with experience in skilled or semi-skilled tasks combined with a reluctance to learn such skills due to the negative perception of manufacturing jobs.

The toll of depression on the UK economy cannot be ignored. The Kings Fund (2012) estimates the cost of depression to the National Health Service (NHS) to be £3 billion per year and rising. Future trends predict increased mental health problems due to increases in solitary and urban lifestyles and a lack of treatment capacity.

If we are becoming depressed as we are not making (Collier, 2011; Lambert, 2006), can this gap in the labour market be addressed while also providing therapeutic benefits and alleviating pressure on the overstrained NHS? If so, most likely a significant shift in attitudes will be required.

Here, the intervention of design thinking and processes can deliver the maximum benefit, helping to change both working conditions and perceptions.

Design for manufacturing awareness

A key task for designers is to raise the public's awareness of the skilled makers who contribute to garment production. In a world of automated production, it is probable that the perception of garment manufacture is of a far less skilled and operator dependent process than it is in reality. Thus, for the makers concerned it becomes a more thankless, impersonal task.

To some degree, luxury and heritage fashion brands are already addressing this issue through their marketing as they attempt to differentiate themselves from mass-produced clothing. Luxury brand Gucci's 'Artisan Corner' events (Gucci, 2012) and a recent exhibition of the work of Hermes' craftspeople (Saatchi Gallery, 2013) both centralised the skilled makers employed by the brands and encouraged the public to interact with them. Stutterheim raincoats, which are individually signed off by the seamstresses who make them (Stutterheim, 2013) are another example.

Can designers go further and create garments which can be made on a mass-produced scale yet highlight the human element of their origins?

Design for makers' benefit

Many of the standards adopted by UK garment manufacturers are intended to maximise efficiency, allowing local production to become more cost effective compared to offshoring. This often results in the tasks an employee undertakes being reduced to single, repetitive 'production line' processes. Research must explore whether such limited variety still affords the maker any psychological benefit, or whether this will also afflict the maker with the 'disease of boredom'. Jackson and Mullarkey (2000) attempt to investigate this through a comparison of the psychological benefits of 'Lean' production teams using the Toyota Sewing System (a form of Quick Response Manufacturing or QRM) and traditional production line systems where bundles of work progress from operator to operator (the Progressive Bundle System or PBS). Despite differences in work design and social context of the two systems, the wellbeing outcomes showed no significant difference between the two. Jackson & Mullarkey (2000) note however that in the factories studied, QRM was the more popular system and could be linked to lower staff turnover.

Despite these findings, UK garment manufacturers generally still use PBS for large-scale production due to lack of recent investment and business innovation; or single operator manufacture of entire garments for small-scale, high-end production. However there is anecdotal evidence that a more group-based system is gradually being adopted. Hopefully, given the related increase in task variety, responsibility for whole garment production and group control amongst manufacturing workers, this may lead to increased emotional wellbeing.

Some Researchers have conversely proposed that repetitive motion may be beneficial for emotional wellbeing and depression (Jacobs, 1994; Riley, Corkhill & Morriss 2013). In Collier's (2011) study, the two most highly ranked reasons for engaging in textile making were enjoyment of the rhythm and repetition (8th most popular) and enjoyment of the sensory experience, including the kinesthetic (3rd most popular).

If there is a significant difference in emotional response between PBS, QRM and whole garment production, how can manufacturing processes be designed for optimum efficiency and to provide sufficient rewards, e.g. the satisfaction of seeing an item you have made in its finished form?

Can Ruitenbergh & Desmet's (2012) categories of Promise Focused design for happiness be collapsed so that both the 'product' and the 'activity' of its creation stimulate happiness, rather than the finished product inspiring happiness or an activity that stimulates it? Perhaps stimulating 'meaningful activities' (Desmet, 2011) at both the manufacturing and end use phases of product lifecycle? This may prove particularly complex as Ruitenbergh & Desmet (2012) note that meaningful activities are highly context and person dependent. Thus, further study of the contexts of garment making and its' manufacturing environments are required.

Prior research into workplace design and psychology has been conducted in office environments, focused on ergonomics and the creation of workers' desired atmosphere (Augustin, 2012). Manufacturing workers have less control over their environment as they may have no fixed workstation. It is therefore all the more vital that designers address the challenge of creating products which will provide them with a beneficial emotional experience during the manufacturing process.

DESIGN RESEARCH CONCERNING GARMENT MAKING AND EMOTION

To address the problematic socioeconomic scenario herein depicted, an ongoing research programme (research questions and methodologies) is proposed below:

- Research Question 1: Do fashion designers and the public accurately perceive how much human input goes into making their clothes?

Methods: An online questionnaire (see: <https://lcf.wufoo.eu/forms/garment-manufacturing-survey/>) is currently being publicised at fashion industry events and disseminated to the public (non-experts) via social media.

- Research Question 2: Can garments be designed which highlight human manufacturing input, raising public awareness and appreciation of garment makers?

Methods: Design gaming studies and triadic comparison (Bang, 2009) will be used to discover whether the public attribute extra manufacturing effort to specific garment finishing techniques and fabrics. Sample garments will be used as elicitation tools. Based on these studies and industry examples of highlighting manufacture, a speculative design process will be used to prototype garments designed to be perceived as involving greater manufacturing effort than their conventional counterparts.

These designs will then be subject to extensive user testing to gain further feedback and be refined through an iterative process.

- Research Question 3: Does garment making on an industrial scale offer emotional and wellbeing benefits similar to those of textile making in occupational therapy? Which garment production method is the most beneficial to the maker?

Methods: The physiological (galvanic skin response) data of makers using PBS, QRM and whole garment production will be tracked along with baseline readings in a relaxed, non-work setting. Qualitative interview data describing their emotional experience will also be recorded. This process will then be applied to textile makers in an occupational therapy context who will be monitored when making, with a baseline taken during other activities. Differences in physiological data between making and baseline activities will then be compared to see if emotional benefit can indeed be observed from garment making in either or both scenarios. Each industrial method and industrial VS occupational making will then be compared, noting physiological indicators of stress levels.

- Research Question 4: Can emotional design or Kansei Engineering processes create a garment that fulfills the needs of the maker during manufacture as well as those of the end consumer?

Methods: Using a similar design research approach to Research Question 2, extensive stakeholder research with garment makers will be conducted to inform speculatively designed garments or manufacturing processes for further testing and iterative development.

CONCLUSION

The proposed research highlights our impoverished understanding of consumers' and makers' perceptions of garments, their finishing and manufacturing processes.

The contribution of the research is to provide greater understanding of garments as a designed product and allow designers to make socially responsible choices around their manufacture, possibly facilitating a return to local production in the UK. Crucially, it will also expand the discipline of emotional design to include designing for the benefit of the maker and not only the end user as Norman (2004) proposes; as if we do not nurture the makers who produce designed products, we risk losing such capacity altogether.

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SIMPLE LIMB INSTITUTE

AN AFFORDABLE PROSTHESIS FOR EVERYONE

Gerhardt Reichert, Leslie Speer

Hochschule für Gestaltung Schwäbisch Gmünd & San José State University

✉ gerhard.reichert@hfg-gmuend.de, leslie.speer@sjsu.edu

ABSTRACT

The Simple Limb Initiative¹ is a project and product delivery system built on the concept of affordability, co-design, cultural and emotional connection, scalability, and open source. Children throughout the world suffering from limb loss due to war, violence, or disease number in the hundreds of thousands². Their need for prosthetics that can grow with them, integrate them back into society, and provide a future of productivity is clear. The Simple Limb Institute website is a place where amputees, their representative, or a service organization can go to download plans for building a prosthesis (arm or leg) from locally sourced materials, using identified local organizations for fitting and rehab, for about the equivalent of US\$30. The selected prosthesis meets cultural and aesthetic norms for the region they live in. The project is in its infancy, with initial concepts developed and available for testing for Colombia, Afghanistan, and Cambodia. Future concepts for Colombia will be developed by May 2014 with plans to expand to several other countries over the next three years.

Connecting a user to the product they live with daily is dependent upon many things – but the ability for a product like a prosthesis to gain emotional integration into the life of a user is what can create a successful life story for a young child. Self-acceptance of their existence as an amputee, acceptance into a family, and integration into a community and a culture – all provide for a thriving life for a young child from their youth through to adulthood. This goal is at the heart of the Simple Limb Institute and through Design, we strive to achieve this goal with our collaborators and future customers.

KEYWORDS: *prosthetic, prosthesis, culture, aesthetic, emotion, co-design*

INTRODUCTION

This project began as a collaborative effort between two professors and their students from the Hochschule für Gestaltung Schwäbisch Gmünd³ in Germany and San José State University⁴ in California. The idea of a US\$30 prosthetic as a goal for a design project for Industrial Design students in their respective institutions drove the development and formation of this collaborative venture. Advanced level students in the respective undergraduate programs review each other's work, share research and data, and participate in WebEx critiques at the end of each phase of the project. The Simple Limb Institute is an ongoing receptacle for good and appropriate design solutions that meet the cultural, emotional, and functional needs of the amputee.

- 1 Simple Limb Initiative Website: <http://simplelimb.com/>
- 2 Unicef: <http://www.unicef.org/graca/mines.htm>
- 3 Hochschule für Gestaltung Schwäbisch Gmünd: <http://www.hfg-gmuend.de/>
- 4 San José State University: www.sjsu.edu

PROJECT PHASES

The project for the course is set up with eight different phases, each one moving the student teams through various design activities with outcomes. A typical stage gate process, as described by Ulrich and Eppinger⁵, is followed and modified where required for this specific project. The phase descriptions and an image that describes the phases are below.

Phase 1 Analyze by reading Case Studies, review the ICRC and their manuals for production of prosthetics, review other manuals for prosthetics (Jaipur Foot, Jaipur Knee, Otto Bock, etc.), research the “place” (Cambodia, Colombia, Afghanistan), the people, the culture, and review ergonomic standards for children ages 5-15.

Phase 2 Reflect by thinking about what was learned from phase 1, get in contact with a local orthopedist to learn more about designing and building prosthetics, contact non-profit

- 5 Ulrich, K. and Eppinger, S., *Product Design and Development*, MacGraw-Hill Irwin, New York, 2011. Pgs. 12-22

organizations to start developing a “partnership” with someone in the country your team is assigned to, talk with amputees (lead users), and start sketching concepts.

Phase 3 Explore by sketching and building and testing out your ideas for functionality. Think about how you could integrate your solution in a business model that incorporates ideas of materials sourcing, building, fitting, training, and rehabilitation, all the steps required for successful prosthesis deployment.

Phase 4 Create testable artifacts for some of your more probable concepts further through prototypes, more detailed drawings, technical drawings, and renderings. Use yourself and your teammates as models to test the durability and functionality of the prototypes (use your testing apparatus to attach to yourselves).

Phase 5 Test your ideas! Get your prototype sent to an amputee or organization in your assigned country so that it can be tested and feedback given. Review the feedback, analyze it and use it to enhance/improve your design in the next phase.

Phase 6 Elaborate your final design ideas into the best appearance/functional prototype possible. This prototype should look like a final product and should also work well enough for someone to test it out. Use the intended materials for the final product and introduce cultural and aesthetic solutions that connect the product to the culture and the people.

Phase 7 Establish a public venue (website) for all the solutions. Organize into country pages and post your ideas for the business structure for fabrication and distribution and provide manuals for production and assembly in a visually cohesive website.

Phase 8 Care for the user/customer by providing a finalized website that includes information about producing, fitting, and training for the implementation of your prosthetics.

PROCESS

Throughout the project, students, amputees, occupational therapists, designers, and engineers worked collaboratively to develop solutions that met basic needs for a child amputee. Each team was assigned a country and the work to assess began.

Business Strategy

The goal is to have each team develop a different business strategy and unique solution that fits the country/culture they are designing for.

Collaboration

Teams are asked to locate a local organization in the country they are designing for. This organization could aid in fabrication or fitting or rehab with amputees. Here are examples found in the project last year⁶:

ICRC: International Council of the Red Cross/Red Crescent (global)

CIREC: Centro Integral de Rehabilitación de Colombia

Fundación Mi Sangre

- 6 ICRC (International Committee of the Red Cross): <http://www.icrc.org/eng/>; CIREC (Centro Integral de Rehabilitación de Colombia): <http://www.cirec.org/>; OMAR (Organization for Mine Clearance and Afghan Rehabilitation): <http://www.omar.org.af/english/>; AHDS (Afghan Health and Development Services): <http://www.ahds.org/>; IFRC (International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent): <https://www.ifrc.org/>; Exceed (formerly known as The Cambodia Trust): <http://www.exceed-worldwide.org/>; USAID: <http://www.usaid.gov/>; Mahavir Kmina: <http://www.mahavir-kmina.org/>; Fundación Sin Manos: <http://www.sinmanos.org/amputado.html>.

Figure 1: Simple Limb Project Process

Simple Limb Initiative project team structure

	Design Strategy #1: made of 100% local materials, resources, labor	Design Strategy #2: made of mix of imported parts, locally made parts/labor	Design Strategy #3: made in China, India, or other hub	Design Strategy #4: other?
Team 1 (4)	XXXX	XXXX	XXXX	XXXX
Team 2 (5)	XXXX	XXXX	XXXX	XXXX
Team 3 (5)	XXXXX	XXXXX	XXXXX	XXXXX
Team 4 (5)	XXXXX	XXXXX	XXXXX	XXXXX
Team 5 (5)	XXXXX	XXXXX	XXXXX	XXXXX

Figure 2: Simple Limb Team Structure and Business Model Structures

Fig 3: Some organizations discovered in the respective countries (Afghanistan, Cambodia, Colombia)

Fig. 4: Knee concept, foot concept, above-knee prosthetic concept.

OMAR: Organization for Mine Clearance and Afghan Rehabilitation

AHDS: Afghan Help and Development Services

RCRC: Rose Charities

The Cambodia Trust

USAID + VI (Veterans Internation)

Foundation Mahavir-Kmina

During the current academic year (SP14) students have successfully developed communication links with Mahavir Kmina and Sin Manos. Teams have been communicating with the organizations through the research and testing phases of their project and have successfully sent 2nd round functional prototypes to the organizations for evaluation of function and robustness. Feedback is currently being received and evaluated as they move towards finalizing their design.

Cultural/Emotional Connection Through Materials and Decoration

Teams investigated each culture, its people, its economy, its arts and industry, its material resources – paying specific attention to the arts and crafts of the regions. From their findings about local infrastructure, local organizations, and local resources and traditions, they were able to move into the concept development phase with an aesthetic direction identified.

Research methods were unique, as student teams were unable to visit any of these countries. San José State University is a deeply diverse institution, with an average of 10-15 different cultures sitting in any one classroom. Campus life includes many student organizations, many of which are set up for ethnically identified groups⁷. Additionally, the diversity of the faculty and administration provides opportunities to talk with recent immigrants and multi-generational households comprised of family members who visit their homeland frequently. Though not as good as doing research in-country, students were able to interview people from Afghanistan, Cambodia, and Colombia and get feedback on their projects from a culturally appropriate lens.

Concepts

Student teams moved through three (3) concept/prototype phases, each one with more and more refinement to the design. Some examples of testing, design inspiration (culture/aesthetic), and materials experiments follow. Initial concepts included concepts and first pass prototypes for knee joints, feet, hands, and different parts of the leg (pylon, socket, ankle). See some of the initial concepts below:

⁷ SJSU Student Clubs: <https://vpsaweb2.sjsu.edu/greenlight/pages/public/directory.php>

Results

Solutions for arm and leg prosthetics were presented at the end of the term. Both above elbow and below elbow prosthetics, along with above knee and below knee solutions, were presented by each team. Testing of the devices was done by construction of adult-scaled prototypes to test on team members. This allowed them to test for strength, movement, robustness, and usability. Teams did assessment of the prototypes, made adjustments to the design, and then right-sized the prototypes and associated instruction manuals for children ages 5-15. The reason children were chosen was two-fold. First, being able to get a child a prosthetic can allow them to continue on in school, receive a basic education, and successfully join the work world. Second, children's growth patterns provide a unique opportunity to design modular solutions that take into account how a child grows and how the prosthesis can change with the child, thereby reducing financial impact on the family with repeated prosthetic replacements.

The result of the project, the first time it was run, provided insights into successful approaches and gave the leadership team ideas on how to approach the project in the future. Although products were primitive, and had some flaws, there were a few successes. Each country had at least one successful concept to go forward to further testing. Multiples of those prototypes are being made to send out for testing now. Concurrently, the live website, with all the product plans are available for download, building and testing, with a provision that the customer provides feedback on the experience of building, fit, use, and learning curve for all aspects of the process.

The Simple Limb Initiative website is live and has generated some interest from other collaborators in the bio-medical programs at different institutions, along with the possibility of receipt of grant funds for further research and testing. The current semester project is focusing solely on Colombia, with projects being developed in both California and Germany, by students in the respective institutions.

Fig. 5: Results of first Simple Limb Initiative project.

FUTURE PLANS

The Simple Limb Initiative is in its infancy. It seeks to find interested collaborators for testing and deployment in the field. Only once the products have reached the children who are amputees, will the project be a success.

It is hoped that with the successful assistance of grant funding, the project leaders will be able to go to Colombia in the summer/fall of 2014 to engage in future research and establish long-term collaborations with local organizations (ICRC, CIREC, Mi Sangre, Sin Manos, and Mahavir Kmina).

Fig 6: Final functional prototypes/models.

Fig 7: Prototypes on model.

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PEERBY.COM

BORROW THE THINGS YOU NEED FROM THE PEOPLE IN YOUR NEIGHBORHOOD

Anna Noyons
Chief Product Officer at Peerby BV
✉ anna@peerby.com

ABSTRACT

This design case reports the process of designing Peerby: an app and website that allows people to borrow the things they need from people in their neighborhood.

It describes how the product concept evolved from an inventory-listed peer-to-peer renting platform to a request-based borrowing and lending platform. We found out that people don't want to rent out things and ask their neighbors for money, but want to help out their neighbors for free. We learned that people are not willing to list their inventory to be able to lend their property, but when asked for a specific object people are very willing to help out a neighbor. We learned that trust and ratings aren't that important when it comes to neighbors and that people in general trust their neighbors easily. All these insights have led to a completely new product vision and design concept.

KEYWORDS: *social cohesion, sustainability, borrowing, platform, service*

INTRODUCTION

Peerby's founder, Daan Weddepohl, who owned a software company, saw his house burn down. In the fire, he lost all of his belongings. Watching the fire he asked himself: 'How did I end up owning all that stuff?' Left with his laptop as his only accessory and means of communication, he depended on the help and generosity of his friends in the weeks that followed.

To his surprise, they all loved to help him out! As a result, he spent valuable time with people he liked, and got to know them better in the process. 'Why don't we do this more often, if it's that easy and fun? Do I even still need stuff, if all I need is my laptop and the people around me?' he thought to himself. And the seed to create a business around this feeling of connectedness, sharing objects and kindness was planted.

This paper reports the design case of a Dutch Internet start up founded in 2011 called Peerby.com. Peerby is a platform that enables people to borrow things from people in their neighborhood. The start-up was founded in late 2011, and the first version went online October 2012. In little more than a year, it has grown to over 40,000 users worldwide, and over 3,000 borrowing transactions per month.

This paper will describe a few of the main insights that lead the design process and design decisions from that project up till today.

DESIGN

Approach

None of the 'designers' of the first version of Peerby were actually familiar with any design method, as they were not trained designers. When the author joined, it felt however as if the ViP (Vision in Product design) method introduced by Hekkert, and van Dijk (2011) is a context driven, human centred, interaction-based design approach. The main focus of the ViP approach is to look for alternatives, and possible futures, instead of solving present-day problems. It highly values the personal vision-creation of the designer (or team) and helps translate this vision into appropriate and suitable user-product interactions. As Peerby was founded by one person, and later created by a small team that shared the same vision, without restrictions in any design-brief or ideation phase whatsoever, the ViP method suited – and still does – our process very well.

After the first vision and conceptualizing phase, it was decided to create an MVP (minimal viable product), a working prototype that only contains the most important features and can be tested and used by real users. All the interaction is measured and from this data we acquire insights about how users behave using the product. Other insights are gained from talking to users and observing behaviour. In software development this method is called the 'Lean Start-up method' (Ries, E. 2011). The knowledge and insights gained from this version are used to build new and improved features, and the team constantly iterates these "build-measure-learn" loops in order to improve the product.

For this paper I will only focus on a few key emotional & psychological insights that have been of great influence on the product concept. I will describe how these factors translated in the product concept and main interactions as well as some new insights that we gained along the way.

First concept - A Peer to Peer Renting Platform

Weddepohls' vision was to create a platform where people that live close to each other can help each other out by sharing the things they own. Initially, the assumption was that people would only do that if they could earn a small sum of money in return. So the first concept of Peerby was a renting platform. Users could list the items that they owned and were willing to rent out, and request any item they needed by typing in the name of the item. The request would then be sent out to all the Peerby users in the neighborhood who had

listed the item. The owner would then be able to chat with the requester to complete the transaction.

MVP – Minimal Viable Product

The first concept was quite elaborate, with features like personal profiles, ratings, product profiles, max radius settings, etc. The Lean start-up method tells you to first create a minimal viable product, in order to test the principles and hypothesis your concept is based on, before spending months developing something that turns out wrong. So, we decided to first create a very simple web-based version of the platform. The payment-method was left out, and people were encouraged to arrange their own prices and deals. Since it was only the very beginning of Peerby, no inventory was listed yet, so it wasn't possible to search for products intelligently by going through peoples' listings. It was decided for now to just send out emails to Peerby-members of everything that was requested until the listing-of-items-system was built and people had had the time to list their inventory. The only two basic functions that were developed were:

1. users could create a request of what they wanted to rent.
2. they could receive requests from neighbors, both through email and on the website at the 'incoming requests' tab (see Figure 04).

For each new request an email was sent to the closest 100 Peerby members, and users could answer "yes", "no" or "not now". If a user answered "yes", she and the requestor would end up in a chat.

Figure 1. Listing the items you would like to rent out.

Figure 2. Requesting an item you would like to rent.

Figure 3. People could send out a request and write something nice to convince their neighbors to lend them something.

Figure 4. Users could receive requests from their neighbors and answer them.

Learnings

From this first product-version we learned many important things about our users that profoundly shaped our product vision, and the next version in particular. A few of the main psychological insights are explained here.

1. People don't want to rent things to their neighbors, they want to help and meet their neighbors.

We encouraged people to rent out things to their neighbors, but they didn't. By analyzing peoples' chats, we learned that almost no one asked for money. The assumption that people need something in return for their helping a neighbor just wasn't valid. Instead we saw that people loved to help out their neighbors. Very often, people got more than three neighbors willing to lend a requested item. Users told us that they liked meeting new neighbors and doing something nice for them. When it comes to neighbors, it turns out people are in fact very altruistic.

2. People don't want to spend time listing their inventory, but when asked, they love to help out, with anything.

People responded very positively to the 'random' requests that we sent out and relatively few people asked us to list their items.

When we looked into it, every single platform we could find that tried to create a borrowing/lending service failed. On average people listed less than one item per member. This is based on an analysis we performed of the borrowing/lending platforms spullendelen.nl, neighborrow.com, neighborgoods.net, and streetbank.com. We did this by dividing the number of members by the number of listed items. The result was always less than one.

Thinking of the proverbial cup of sugar, 'normal' borrowing usually happens only when the borrower experiences an often sudden need, and asks his or her neighbor for a favor. From the lender's perspective, if the favor is granted, the deed is reactive rather than proactive. It seems like people do like to help out someone in need, but are not very willing to spend a lot of time anticipating that possibility.

In fact, when you think about the process of borrowing, how often does one wonder, going over all the things in and around the house, 'Gosh, I wish someone would come and borrow these things from me'?

By creating a platform that was request based, we tapped into something that did work and suited the borrowing/lending principles much better.

Figure 5. Streetbank. On average people never list more than one item to lend.

Figure o6. Screenshots of the current iOS app

3. Trust – people naturally trust their neighbors and violation occurs very seldom.

The first Peerby concept had a very elaborate trust and rating system. People were able to report other users in case of violation, and review/rate their neighbors. People could leave a deposit. In the MVP there were no such things. The product was in that sense very ‘risky’ and open. To our surprise, people didn’t care that much. Usually borrowers (people that sent out a request) were already so pleased by the kind offers of their neighbors that that was enough to trust someone. And lenders were also very willing to help out, without knowing anything about the other member. ‘Rating’ a person that just lent you something for free, didn’t quite fit the situation. We did, however, discover that borrowers felt a strong need to publicly (on a profile) thank the lender for his/her kindness. Also publishing how long someone had been a member, along with her activity also made sense. Of all the transactions that we had on the platform (over 10.000), we know of only three cases where things were not returned or broken and left unresolved.

4. People fear being rejected when asking for a favor directly.

In ‘real life’ as a borrower, you have to ask your neighbor for a favor. You have to go over, ring a bell and ask for something. By directly asking this favor, one runs the risk of being a burden to your neighbor or your neighbor just not being willing to lend you something and thus being rejected. This anticipated feeling of discomfort makes borrowing a rather risky and therefore potentially uncomfortable action and this could contribute to people borrowing less than they would like to. The market-place inventory model for borrowing and lending does not change that; you need to ask your neighbors (whom you don’t know) for a favor directly, by personally requesting an item, running the risk of being rejected. But the way we sent out our requests (to 100 people) avoided this risk. Because as a borrower you would not know who was asked (we don’t give that feedback) and people could freely say NO without insulting someone. The borrower is only notified about the few people that said yes and this is only a very positive experience.

CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION – A REQUEST-BASED BORROWING AND LENDING PLATFORM

From a peer-to-peer renting service, Peerby has evolved in the only working borrowing/lending platform in the world. We learned a huge amount from our first version of the product, and we are now planning to build a completely revised mobile (android) version of the app. The focus on borrowing, and the request-based interaction, have become key. The open system based on trusting your neighbors (i.e., no ratings) is also very important. We have also learned about what people think is still missing in the product. For example, people want to know what is happening on Peerby in their neighborhood. They want to interact in more ways than just saying “yes”, “no” or “not now” to their neighbors’ needs. In some cases they do want to list special items. And, most of all, people want to be inspired by being able to ‘browse’ through things they could possibly borrow. Our main short-term challenge will be to stimulate people to request things and make borrowing from their neighbors a new habit. We learned that people love to lend. Our transaction success rate at the moment is 83%! Another challenge is to create a self-learning inventory system so that we can search in smarter ways and thus improve fulfillment even further.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Although I have written this article, all of the thinking and hard work has been done by the whole Peerby team including founder, Daan Weddepohl, Eelke Boezeman, Ieteke Schouten, Dirk van Oosterbosch and many others.

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ZONEA/ZONE1: REFLECTION/RESILIENCE

David Frisco, Andrew Shea
 Graduate Communications Design Department, Pratt Institute
 ✉ dfrisco@pratt.edu, ashea18@pratt.edu

ABSTRACT

ZoneA/Zone1: Reflection/Resilience was a 13 week classroom investigation into community based resiliency efforts and awareness in NYC one year after Superstorm Sandy. Our initiative asked how might communication designers enable individuals and communities along the coastline of New York City to adapt and become more resilient in face of climate change.

Using the *NYC Special Initiative for Rebuilding and Resiliency (SIRR) Report*¹ as a departure point, we engaged with the five most affected communities in NYC through cultural probes and interventions, addressing each area's unique relationship to the city's waterfront and much-needed resiliency efforts.

With an emphasis on a human-centered, holistic, and empathic approach, our teams applied Design Thinking methodologies to social issues aiming to transform behaviors of individuals and communities in desirable, sustainable ways, while creating meaningful experiences and interactions that promote disaster preparedness.

KEYWORDS: *New York City, Superstorm Sandy, Climate Change, Resiliency, Social Impact*

INTRODUCTION

“Superstorm Sandy, on October 29, 2012, directly affected a wide variety of diverse social, economic and physical communities along the coastline of the New York City region. Low- and moderate- income families inhabit many areas that were adversely affected, as do many small businesses and manufacturing establishments. Other communities that are vulnerable to related climate change events were spared, but they too need to be better prepared for the future.”²

ZoneA/Zone1: Reflection/Resilience was a 13 week classroom investigation into community based resiliency efforts and awareness in NYC one year after Superstorm Sandy. Our study was conducted from September to December 2013, overlapping with the one year anniversary of Sandy's touchdown on New York City's shores.

ZoneA/Zone1 asks how might communication designers enable individuals and/or communities along the coastline of New York City to adapt and become more resilient in face of climate change.

- <http://www.nyc.gov/html/sirr/html/report/report.shtml>
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Figure 1. Hurricane Sandy NOAA/NWS Radar image and NYC OEM Evacuation Zone Map

ASSIGNMENT

ZoneA/Zone1 took place during the Fall 2013 semester of Transformation Design, a Graduate Communications Design MFA Studio, at Pratt Institute, lead by instructors David Frisco and Andrew Shea.

Using the *NYC Special Initiative for Rebuilding and Resiliency (SIRR) Report*³ as a departure point, our teams engaged with the five most affected communities in NYC through qualitative research in the form of cultural probes and interventions, addressing each area's unique relationship to the city's waterfront and impacting climate change, ultimately creating a set of proposals and, in some cases, implementing solutions and toolkits serving to improve grass-root resiliency efforts in each community.

Our objective was to design a responsive communication strategy as well as individual or community-led activities that advanced resiliency efforts and foster behavior change, putting preparedness at the fore. The goal was to inspire and engage a community to take action.

We concentrated on the following five communities identified in the NYC Special Initiative for Rebuilding and Resiliency (SIRR) Report: *A Stronger, More Resilient New York*

- Brooklyn-Queens Waterfront
- East and South Shores of Staten Island
- South Queens
- Southern Brooklyn
- Southern Manhattan

PROCESS

Our initiative focused on qualitative research strategies to utilize design as a means for transformation. With an emphasis on a human-centered, holistic, and empathic approach, our teams applied Design Thinking methodologies to localized problems and issues in an attempt to transform the behaviors of individuals in desirable and sustainable ways, while creating meaningful experiences and interactions.

Emphasizing that people are participants rather than simply users, we studied human factors — cognitive, physical, emotional, linguistic, social and cultural behaviors. We explored numerous conceptual and procedural frameworks which guide the design process, in order to address the needs of people and organizations, and convert them into progressive, sustainable solutions.

Our investigation was conducted over 13 weeks — from September to December, 2013 — we divided our work into four distinct phases.

3 <http://www.nyc.gov/html/sirr/html/report/report.shtml>

Figure 2: Native-speaking Chinese students were able to have informal conversations and interview local Chinatown residents.

Phase 1: Research

Teams were formed and self-assigned specific roles with the groups such as, community outreach, photographer/videographer, designer, producer and fabricator to name just a few.

Preliminary Research

At the onset of the project we lead with a spontaneous study: 30 questions about post-Sandy to the immediate and general public. While all teams asked strangers, each approach varied. Some asked people to stop and talk to them, but the more successful examples were when students used empathetic interview approaches and asked people who were stationary (street vendors, doormen, etc.), or walked with people and asked questions while en route.

Primary Research

At this stage we introduce a number of human-centered, empathic research methodologies prevalent in the design industry. IDEO's *HCD Toolkit*⁴, Frog Design's *Collective Action Toolkit*⁵, Stanford dSchool's *Bootcamp Bootleg*⁶ and Jon Kolko's *Wicked Problems Worth Solving*⁷ all offer strategies for first-hand, qualitative design research that promotes empathy and helps to identify trends, patterns, insights and innovative opportunities for design.

Phase 2: Concepting and Prototyping

During the synthesis stage of primary research, we introduced our teams to John Belienberg's Think Wrong⁸ exercise as a way to think divergently. This encouraged our team to "break the biases and synaptic pathways that subconsciously lead to predictable solutions" and allowed for multiple cre-

4 <http://www.ideo.com/work/human-centered-design-toolkit/>

5 <http://www.frogdesign.com/work/frog-collective-action-toolkit.html>

6 <http://dschool.stanford.edu/wp-content/uploads/2011/03/BootcampBootleg2010v2SLIM.pdf>

7 <https://www.wickedproblems.com/>

8 <http://www.projectmlab.com/Think-Wrong>

Figure 3: Students designed public interventions that engaged with the community.

Figure 4: Students conducting research via participatory public intervention with Chinatown residents.

Figure 5: Students partnered with Vision 20/20 to instantiate their interactive games geared towards Coney Island youth.

Figure 6: Resilience Extravaganza Toolkit encourages schools to create their own games and incorporate into curriculum.

ative directions for our cultural probes or public interventions, scheduled for October 29th, the one year anniversary of Superstorm Sandy.

Phase 3: Implementation

To learn from our interventions, delivery theories as defined by IDEO’s HCD Toolkit were presented at this stage. Teams were encouraged to work directly with their communities to form partnerships to launch their final designs and toolkits. In certain cases, connecting to local politicians and community boards was the appropriate strategy for implementation.

Phase 4: Assessment and Evaluation

As a final step towards maximizing impact, resources like Keystone Accountability’s Impact Planning, Assessment and Learning Method⁹, taken from IDEO’s HCD Toolkit, that encourage holistic impact assessment were introduced. Toolkits were created to extend the impact of the project outward beyond the individual instances. Conventional ways to track and measure the design solutions through websites, interviews, and ongoing feedback collection are also employed as a means to measure success.

⁹ <http://www.keystoneaccountability.org/analysis/ipl>

PROJECT DESCRIPTIONS

Chinatown

Chinatown 2020 is an activity to help Greater Chinatown in NYC to be more resilient towards the severe climate change such as Hurricane Sandy. Because card games are popular with the elderly in Columbus Park, our solution took this form in its playfulness and ease, as it reaches our target audience. The audience can use the 2020 cards not only as typical playing cards, but also as conversation openers around preparedness. Moreover, it provides bilingual disaster tips.

Students: Karl Davies, Xiao Han, Ji Eun Lee, Lillian Ling, Eduardo Palma

Red Hook

Red Hook is a low-lying neighborhood located on the Brooklyn waterfront. The neighborhood was deeply impacted by Hurricane Sandy in 2012 and is still recovering from the effects of the storm. The community feels neglected by the city as in the aftermath of the storm most of the help came from volunteers and community members.

Red Hook Helps is a system aimed at facilitating communication in times of storms and hurricanes. The toolkit seeks to

Figure 7: Chinatown 2020 Final Review summary poster

empower and amplify the voice of an already tight-knit community, allowing its members to connect and help each other more easily.

Students: Bárbara Abbès, Rogier Bak, Xiaoping Ma, Amanda Sepanski

Rockaways

Activate: Fostering Access to Healthcare in the Rockaways is a campaign facilitated by a small group of Graduate Communication Design students, invaluable guided and assisted by a number of Rockaways residents, community groups and local activists. The goal of the campaign is to rally the people of the Rockaways around the healthcare system and demand an increase in accessible healthcare options, resulting in widespread civic engagement and ultimately a more resilient community in the face of disaster.

St. John's Episcopal Hospital is the lone remaining hospital on the Rockaway Peninsula. Though designed to serve 15,000 people annually, it has seen to the needs of nearly three times that number in the year since Sandy's devastating assault on the Rockaways. This single facility has to accommodate the 130,000 residents of the area and simply cannot keep up with the staffing and economic demands that it is met with. Superstorm Sandy struck a crippling blow to St. John's; already

Figure 8: Red Hook Helps Final Review summary poster

struggling financially before the storm, the hospital provided free care to many residents in its wake and has yet to be reimbursed for most of these costs.

The hospital, and more importantly the community, is not ready for another natural disaster like Sandy. As we reflect on the storm's impact one year later, it is startling to see how ill-prepared we are to survive something similar in the future. The Rockaways is an isolated community; if routes of transportation are damaged in a storm, residents will have only a single, already overburdened hospital to rely on for emergency healthcare. Area healthcare professionals have expressed a desire for an additional emergency care facility with the ability to transfer patients in need of longer term care to ease some of the hospital's burden.

We designed an interactive experience as a method of engaging the public in this issue. A person navigates a situation in which they need to obtain health care after a natural disaster, encountering a number of obstacles and barriers along the way. Ideally, the game builds empathy, therefore increasing engagement and prompting action. This experience led to a guidebook, toolkit, and overall system that can ultimately live within and be leveraged by members of the community who wish to stage a similar, in-person, interactive intervention.

ONE YEAR AFTER SANDY, THE HEALTHCARE SYSTEM IN THE ROCKAWAYS STILL ISN'T EQUIPPED TO HANDLE ANOTHER DISASTER.

MAZE

After reviewing all of the research we gathered from Rockaways residents and community connectors, we decided to design a game resembling the labyrinth someone might face when trying to access healthcare in the aftermath of a natural disaster. Eight scenarios were presented in a series of virtual situations around a pre-determined area, each featuring a different colored search path. People passing by were invited to take part in the experience. Through the game, they are prompted to send an email to Letitia James, outlining the steps they would take to resolve the situation. This experience was ultimately designed to be an attempt to simulate a real-world scenario; participants would encounter dead ends or be forced to wait before proceeding to the next step. Upon completion, the participants were given a card that provided the location, contact information, and service hours of the healthcare system accessible on the peninsula. The idea behind the physical component of our campaign, an opportunity to take an immediate step towards action.

FRIENDS

A special thanks to the wonderful organizations that helped us along the way: Rockaway Healthcare Alliance, Respond and Relieff, Rockaway Healthcare Alliance, Rockaway Youth Sea Team, You are Never Alone (NYHA), Sun Brown + John (City of Kings of Columbus)

KRISTEN MYERS

JOHN HALLMAN

TRANSFORMATION DESIGN FALL 2013

ZHITONG ZENG

ALICIA BURNETT

Figure 9: Activate Rockaways Final Review summary poster

Students: Alicia Burnett, John Hallman, Kristen Myers, Zhitong Zeng

Staten Island

Collective Toolbox is a project that seeks to provide Staten Island residents with tools to empower the building of a stronger and more resilient community. Working in collaboration with the Staten Island Long-Term Recovery Organization, the Collective Toolbox team learned from the community about a dire need for tools directly after Superstorm Sandy as cause by flooding in basements and tool sheds where the majority of Staten Islanders would store their tools. Much to the surprise of the team, the Staten Island community still expressed a need for tools over a year after Sandy occurred. Working much like a library, the Collective Toolbox is designed open access to basic tools to the communities across Staten Island.

Students: John Lunn, Juan Rodriguez, Trang Tran, Robert Wilson

Coney Island

From our Classroom

We were asked to design a responsive communication strategy and/or community-led activities that can advance post-Sandy resilience and preparedness efforts in South Brooklyn.

RESEARCH

IDENTIFYING THE PROBLEM
As an initial research step, we visited the Rockaways and conducted interviews with residents and followed up with interviews of community organizations. We conducted a search of local emergency health care options as a first step to identify the gaps in service change.

RESEARCH
St. John's Episcopal Hospital is the largest hospital on the Rockaway Peninsula. Designed to serve 12,000 patients annually, the hospital received 6,000 patients in 2013. Superstorm Sandy struck a major blow to St. John's already struggling financially before the storm, as hospital-provided care was severely impacted. Superstorm Sandy struck a major blow to St. John's already struggling financially before the storm, as hospital-provided care was severely impacted. Superstorm Sandy struck a major blow to St. John's already struggling financially before the storm, as hospital-provided care was severely impacted.

REFINEMENT - COLLABORATION
After identifying and researching our problem, we brainstormed potential courses of action and reached out again to our community contacts for their informed thoughts and feedback. Not only did they provide useful suggestions as we refined our ideas, they later helped promote our campaign through their social media networks.

SYNTHESIS
It was incredibly important to create a campaign that would ultimately give access to critical resources and support to our community contacts for their informed thoughts and feedback. Not only did they provide useful suggestions as we refined our ideas, they later helped promote our campaign through their social media networks.

REFINEMENT - COLLABORATION
After identifying and researching our problem, we brainstormed potential courses of action and reached out again to our community contacts for their informed thoughts and feedback. Not only did they provide useful suggestions as we refined our ideas, they later helped promote our campaign through their social media networks.

CAMPAIGN

Inventory, Public Advocate and current NYC Councilmember Letitia James has been a proponent of accessible health care in all parts of the city. Since she began her first term in citywide office, she has supported the idea of a campaign during her time as Public Advocate and seeking a considerable amount of influence. With this in mind, we decided to focus our outreach efforts on her, we designed a grassroots and crowd-sourced campaign asking her to champion the idea of providing accessible health care options in the Rockaways. With the help of our friends in the community, we composed a pre-written message that residents could send to her, though we also provided flash cards on that people could write out their own message if they wished.

These cards were given out at the end of our maze and the email version was hosted on our website. We stamped and mailed all of the postcards we received and also hosted cards with it community leaders who were interested. Finally, we tracked all of the emails sent to Letitia James.

TOOLKIT

To make it easier for others to replicate and improve our maze we created a downloadable toolkit. We included steps to print templates for the search board's game boards, postcard templates, and healthcare maps to assist in generating products. The toolkit explains the use of various visual elements on the maze to help in the construction, setup and operation of the experience.

Figure 10: Collective Toolbox Final Review summary poster

Our initial research and interviews in the community revealed that while many resources were available, people were uninformed and confused about both storm preparedness and recovery. Inspired by Coney Island's history and identity as America's playground, we were interested in engaging the public in these issues of resiliency with a series of spectacles.

To PS329

We partnered with 20/20 Vision for Schools, an organization dedicated to mobilizing students and community stakeholders for sustainable change, to host an initial iteration of our games at PS329 (at a larger event, the Resilience Mural Ribbon Cutting). It was an occasion for the community to learn, provide feedback and connect to neighbors while having fun. Students played Preparedness Plinko, an educational game that addresses what to do before, during and after a storm. Wonder Ring is a ring-toss game that gave students an opportunity to share what they know, think or wonder on a wall. Dam It? and Gate It? were voting mechanisms to measure the community's adult response to two major initiatives in the NYC Special Initiative for Rebuilding and Resiliency Report.

To Your Classroom

Because of the event's success, we decided to create a toolkit that can help educators recreate an event like ours so they can advance the resilience conversation in schools. We

adjusted our initial ideas to be classroom-friendly, and the carnival games now support three core areas — education, voice and advocacy.

These align with the three domains of Bloom’s Taxonomy, which divides learning objectives into cognitive, affective, and psychomotor (sometimes loosely described as knowing/head, feeling/heart and doing/hands, respectively) categories for a holistic form of education. Remembering, understanding, applying, analyzing, evaluating and creating are the stages of learning, and creating from what you learn is considered to be the highest order thinking skill. The Dam It? and Gate It? activity we created initially evolved into Show of Hands for the classroom. It is a customizable voting mechanism and intra-school advocacy tool that is intended to develop out of the students’ interests as they surface from the Wonder Ring game. Our goals are to promote individual preparedness efforts, to spark dialogue within the school community, to gather feedback from youth and to ultimately foster behavior change.

Our toolkit provides descriptions, background research and making/playing instructions for each of the activities. Educators are encouraged to make the games with the students. Our website sandybros.org both hosts the toolkit and serves as a site for documentation and case studies of the toolkit’s usage

Students: *Rachna Batra, Jonathan Frey, Jeannette Hodgkins, Diego Zaksesi*

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RESEARCH & PROCESS

- Interviews in the South Brooklyn community revealed that while many resources were available, people were unfamiliar about both storm preparedness and current recovery and resiliency efforts.
- Inspired by Corey Island’s history and identity as America’s playground, we were interested in engaging the public in these issues of resiliency with a series of spectacles.
- The visual language and branding of the Resilience Extravaganza borrowed from Corey Island’s identity.
- Searching for locations and speaking with local organizations like Alliance for Green Buildings and Construction led us into the realm of education.

ONE YEAR LATER

On November 2, we hosted an initial iteration of our games at PS209 as part of the Resilience Mural Ribbon Cutting celebration. It was an occasion for the community to learn, provide feedback and connect to neighbors while having fun.

- Preparedness Plinko allowed students the opportunity to reflect on what they know about safety and preparedness while learning more. The questions in the game address what to do before, during and after a storm.
- Wonder Ring gave students an opportunity to play ring toss and share what they know, think or wonder on a wall. The goal of this activity is to spark thought and dialogue in an engaging way.
- Dam It? and Gate It? prompted adults to vote on two major initiatives from the city’s A Stronger, More Resilient New York plan.

AND BEYOND

We have created a toolkit that can help educators recreate an event like ours so they can advance the resilience conversation in schools. The carnival games support three core areas—education, voice and advocacy.

- The games align with Bloom’s Taxonomy, which divides learning objectives into cognitive, affective, and psychomotor categories for a holistic form of education.
- We evolved the Dam It?/Gate It? mechanism into Show of Hands, a customizable polling system and intraschool advocacy tool that develops out of students’ interests and concerns as they surface from a sharing activity (like Wonder Ring).
- Our partnership with 100 No Vision for Schools, an organization dedicated to mobilizing students and community stakeholders for sustainable change, will aid us in testing and disseminating the toolkit to more schools in New York City.

SANDYBROS.ORG
Rachna Batra, Jeannette Hodgkins, Jonathan Frey and Diego Zaks

Figure 11: Resilience Extravaganza Final Review summary poster

DESIGN OF INTERACTIONS FOR SOCIAL APPROPRIATION OF KNOWLEDGE

José Augusto Ocampo A.
 Corporación Parque Explora, Medellín, Colombia
 ✉ jose.ocampo@parqueexplora.org

ABSTRACT

This article presents a case study of Parque Explora's most recent museographic renovation project, which reflects the intentions of a team that aimed to stimulate visitors' appropriation of tools for the creation of contents, resulting in the interactive exhibit *On Stage: Stories behind Stories (En Escena: Historias tras las historias)*, launched at the end of 2013. It demonstrates how, through the area of design, it is possible to contribute to the development of scientific ability, public appropriation of knowledge and the building of citizenship, reinforcing both the Parque Explora as an interactive museum and its role as a "Knowledge Broker" within the ecosystem of innovation in the city of Medellín.

KEY WORDS: *Museography, design, social appropriation, education, innovation*

INTRODUCTION

Starting in 1960, science museums began to radically change their approach, placing special emphasis on providing visitors with a direct experience with physical, natural and technical phenomena. This was done under the assumption that it would allow these visitors to strengthen their confidence and capacity to understand the world around them. (Allen, 2004)

The era's interest in transforming the education system proposed interactivity as an answer to the necessity of learning based on experience and not solely on content. Artifacts were designed (Franco-Avellaneda, 2013) with the aim of presenting and permitting the interaction of visitors with certain phenomena through *interactive* exhibits. Since then, museographers have found themselves facing a series of challenges when creating some of these spaces: with the visitor in mind, the exhibits should facilitate his learning, support him in decision-making (where to go, what to do, and how to understand his interactions) and motivate him at each step of the interaction. This challenge also requires that the design process be supported, from an early stage, by a strong research and evaluation program. (Allen & Gutwill, 2004)

In a similar manner the Parque Explora, an interactive museum in the city of Medellín, has understood and taken on these challenges in the development of its exhibits, through a design process that is based on a work paradigm (Jaramillo, 2011) where the horizontal dialogue between the *what* and the *how* are maintained throughout each project, searching

for equilibrium between contents and stimuli through conversations between museologists, museographicists, scientists, researchers, and the public.

THE RENOVATION

As a science museum located in the city of Medellín, the Parque Explora is a space dedicated to creating stimuli for the visitor. It aims to encourage the public appropriation of knowledge, the development of scientific ability, and the building of citizenship through a renewed offer of permanent and temporary exhibits for its public.

ON STAGE: *Stories behind Stories* is an interactive space, with 900 square meters distributed over two floors, where visitors experiment with different means of expression (communication). Through the use of close to 35 analogue, digital, individual and collective experiences, the visitor produces content under the premise of learning by doing: as he experiments, the visitor gains awareness and appropriates knowledge. (Aguirre et. al., 2013)

More than understanding the way the communication devices and technologies work, the room aims to provide an immersive and personalized experience. It is an exhibit created for a diverse public, as one of the premises in the design was not to base itself on previously held knowledge of its visitors, but on the emotions derived from their interactions with the phenomena, objects, metaphors, and scenographies. (Figure 1)

Figure 1. Panoramic photo of the exhibition.

A MACHINE THAT CREATES WORLDS

The place that contains an exhibit, unlike any other spaces, is characterized by being a complement to a series of objects, both as a container and as a transmitting vehicle. The space is an essential element, which recreates three dimensionally, the coexistence between object, place, atmosphere and meaning. (Perez, 2007).

This new exhibit is not a space dedicated to information and communication technologies (ITC), but a space to be used for expression and creation, where stories take precedence over technique. The museographic design, then, is meant to use discussion and the different graphic, object and spatial languages to stimulate creativity, expressivity, and individual and collective experimentation.

Conceptually, the exhibit is viewed as a stage, where the visitor is creator, actor and audience; the theater is viewed as a physical configuration, where the stage comes to life due to the sum of events, actions and effects that are produced through the spaces and mechanisms that are found around the stage. The interactive room, seen as a whole, is a great machine that creates worlds, that creates stories. (Figure 2)

The interior space is revealed through beams of warm light, the metallic support structures blend with the shadows to reveal the wood, the objects, the titles, and the scenes, all blended together in virtual spaces, visible spaces, that do not intimidate but instead invite. The visitor traverses the space freely, following his own interests, finding out and creating his own interpretations.

Figure 2. Images of the concept of the interactive room.

Figure 3. Visualization of the space. Conceptual approximation.

In each scene, the objects are converted into tools. The space is a workshop, a place for creation and co-creation, from experimentation with camera effects to shadow play and anything between and including rotoscopy, acoustics, video games, discourses, and content for social networks, etc. (Figure 3)

Thus an exhibition is proposed where multiple situations are simultaneously rolled out in each of the spaces through interactive experiences. With a theatrical conceptual base, the experiences are grouped into four zones: Effects, Representation, Discourse and Behind the Scenes. Each one of these interactive experiences is selected because it presents the same possibilities of museographic and museologic dialogue, always keeping in mind the essential criterion of interactivity.

INTERACTIVE SCENES

Interactivity signifies dialogue (Wagensberg, 2001); it is the reciprocity of action, where the visitor acts and the exhibit responds in some way (Allen et al., 2004). This dialogue is physical-emotional and it manifests itself in the interrelation between form, function, and technology experienced over time (Kolko, 2011).

Through horizontal dialogues between content and form, the design team looks to create attractive, functional, useful pieces and at the same time generate compelling and motivating interactions. Going farther than third dimensionality, the team also designs in a fourth dimension: time.

The time considerations allow the designers, from early on in the process, to imagine how the visitor will approach the artifacts: how his attention will be attracted, how he understands their functioning, what kind of actions must be carried out, and what emotions or sensations are brought out in the users and experienced in an individual and/or collective way.

During the development of the project through the use of prototypes, evaluations with a live public are vital in order to verify and redefine the interactions, making sure that the final result works as an effective vehicle and generator of stimuli towards the social appropriation of knowledge.

Based on the *total interactivity* model of Wagensberg (2000), this exhibit employs museographic elements to simultaneously generate three kinds of stimuli in the visitor: sensory stimuli, creative stimuli, and social stimuli. Thus:

- **Sensory stimuli:** The visitor is considered an active element within the exhibition. Experiences are designed to interact with the body and stimulate the senses, where pleasure is generated by the provocation of nature and the response produced.
- **Creative stimuli:** The goal is that the visitor should find common elements within diversity among spaces designed for exploration, discovery, and creation.
- **Social stimuli:** Experiences meant to promote participation and collective interaction through provocative and embracing spaces. In many cases, interactions take on meaning or are completed when they are shared with others.

All of these stimuli are intertwined in each interactive experience. A person may feel himself or herself visually attracted to a space. Once in contact with the space, the person becomes interested in understanding what it is about and presses the bright red button. He decides to experiment and is surprised by the result obtained. He reflects on what happened and tries again, finally sharing the experience with others and initiating conversations.

Below, two interactive experiences developed for this project will be presented as examples to illustrate each of the stimuli previously mentioned.

Example 2: Minor Stories: In a Given Moment

There is an interactive video game equipped with a tangible interface using a mapping projection technique on a relief table. An aboriginal community on an island is created, where there are plants, animals, villagers and a shaman who prays to the heavens when facing an intense summer or a harsh winter. The visitors share complete control of the situation, moving and rotating objects around the projected surface. Handling these objects, the visitors can create different situations: they may change the day into night, summer into winter, create bird and UFO effects, and even inflict natural disasters on specific regions. (See figure 4)

Figure 4. Photograph of visitor interacting with cubes to modify the virtual environment.

- **Sensory Stimuli:** The video projection on a relief surface surprises the visitor, who also finds himself with some objects that allow him to interact with the game in a new and tangible manner.
- **Creative Stimuli:** Each visitor is invited to experiment and create his/her own short story.
- **Social Stimuli:** Three people may simultaneously share the experience and observe the results.

Example 2: Gestures: Distinguishing Marks

An emergency situation at a nuclear power plant is reenacted to incentivize group communication through gestures and to resolve a problem. One of the participants enters a cabin that simulates an alarm situation and only this participant has ac-

Figure 5. Photograph of visitors using gestures to solve a challenge.

cess to the command control; the participants that are in front of the cabin give him instructions through gestures (through a soundproof window), in the hope that he will deactivate the alarm by following a sequence of steps. (See figure 5)

- **Sensory Stimuli:** An emergency situation at a Soviet nuclear power plant is reenacted, conserving the aesthetic and visual language, and therefore giving a tangible and realistic dimension to the experience. The sensation is made more intense and immersive with sound and light effects.
- **Creative Stimuli:** The result depends on the effectiveness, resourcefulness and histrionism of the characters.
- **Social Stimuli:** A challenge is posed through the detection of a communications system failure at the plant; it may only be resolved collectively and through non-verbal language.

STIMULI FOR APPROPRIATION

These stimuli go beyond the pleasure or fun of interacting with the exhibition; they are only worthwhile if they are able to motivate the visitor to enquire, to reach his own conclusions and interpretations, and to relate the experience with his own life. A good science museum is above all an instrument for social change. "... the principal function of a museum is that the visit changes (the visitor's) life. If (he) has more questions when (he) exits than when (he) enters, it is a good sign." (Wagensberg et.al., 2006).

CLOSING COMMENTS

This article reflects the intentions of a multidisciplinary team that designed a museography renovation project for the Parque Explora called *On Stage: Stories behind Stories* (*En Escena: Historias tras las historias*), a process that is enriched by horizontal conversations between the what and the how. These dialogues allow the team to conceive of a welcoming space that is, on the one hand, conceptually forceful and stimulating, and, on the other hand, allows for the design and development of a series of objects and interactive pieces, "scenes", that stimulate creativity, histrionics, and collective participation.

Special emphasis was placed on interactivity — the dialogue between the visitor and the exhibition. Three types of necessary stimuli were considered for the development of the interactive exhibit: social, sensory, and creative stimuli, that are only valuable if they act as motivating vehicles towards the public appropriation of knowledge, scientific ability, and the building of citizenship. This meticulous and conscientious work that took the development team almost two years to complete, has begun to bear fruit several months after being open to the public. The smiles of the visitors, their surprised faces, and their capacity to create, express and share with others, indicate growth emerging from what has been sowed by the stimuli. It is now necessary to examine these positive indications through an evaluation process.

On Stage: Stories behind Stories is a great machine that creates stories from memories that extend beyond the boundaries of the museum. It is a space where design contributes to the strengthening of Parque Explora's role as a "knowledge broker" in the city's ecosystem of innovation, recently recognized internationally as the "most innovative in the world". The interpretation of "innovation" in this case is more directed towards the social construction of knowledge, by sparking in its citizens creative stimuli from the multiple stories that are created in the exhibition.

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POSTURAROMA - THE EMBODIMENT OF SAFETY

Marco van Hout, Laura Mul, Loes Bogers, Shinichiro Ito
 MediaLAB Amsterdam, Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences, School of Design and Communication
 ✉ m.van.hout@hva.nl, lauramul21@gmail.com, lbogers@hva.nl, shinichiro.shin1ro@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This paper introduces a design case that was built around the challenge to design a prototype for women that would positively influence their perception of personal safety in public spaces. The proposed design combines an individual focus with a public impact, influencing emotions through embodiment by introducing a necklace that reminds the wearer to walk straight and as a result, influence felt emotions such as confidence and prevent feelings of unsafety caused by slouching. In this paper, a prototype for wearable technology called PosturAroma is introduced: a fashionable necklace with a sensor that detects slouched body posture and reminds the user to stand straight by giving out a discrete scent.

KEY WORDS: *embodiment, scent, perception of safety, wearable technology*

INTRODUCTION

People are programmed to shape and alter their own personal environment according to their needs and in favor of their personal wellbeing. In order to effectively design any public space it is therefore vital to have an understanding of the needs that the space should meet. Safety increases the comfort of a space (Loukaitou-Sideris, 2005) and attention to features that reduce threats to safety supports this (Farrington, 2002). However, the success of designing for safety (and avoid crime) in public spaces is limited, mostly due to a simplistic understanding of crime perception (Koskela, 2000). Crime statistics often show a gap between safety perception (how safe do people feel) and the objective safety (actual crime statistics) (Carr, 1992).

Objective safety can be improved by preventing unwanted behavior and emotions (Eysink Smeets et al, 2011). For example, applications that intend to prevent teenagers from congregating and misbehaving in specific areas are: the Mosquito (a device sending out an uncomfortable high frequency tone that only younger people can hear) and pink street lighting (said to have a calming influence, but also embarrassingly highlights skin blemishes). However, applications that positively influence safety perception in public spaces are scarce, or lack empirical support. This might be the result of a lack of focus on the individual side of experienced and perceived personal safety.

INFLUENCES ON FEELINGS OF PERSONAL SAFETY IN PUBLIC SPACES

Feeling safe in public spaces is often seen as a result of a combination of the design of the environment and the social control that is present in the space. The latter is today mostly measured by the amount of security cameras that are around. However, research has shown that the presence of cameras has no real positive effect on the feeling of safety (Bannister, Fyfe & Kearns, 1998). Actually, the results illustrated an equal increase in feelings of safety as well as of unsafety. It is necessary to look beyond the space itself and the amount of security; this paper will, therefore, explain how the individual can or does influence his or her own feelings of safety. More specifically, the body, its movements and posture will be taken as a central focal point.

The Influence of Body Posture on Feelings of Personal Safety

According to Damasio's somatic marker hypothesis (1999), emotions are provoked by communicating the current state of the body to the brain. This would imply that deliberately moving in a specific manner could regulate or influence feelings. Other researchers have underlined this by showing that happy, sad or fearful movements indeed evoked these particular emotions (Shafir, Taylor & Atkinson, 2013).

In self-defence training, people are often advised to walk with confidence and not to look scared or unsure (Lorden, 2003, p.7). They are told also to stay alert and aware and look around (Jacob, 2014). When a person looks around, makes eye contact and has the back facing the wall, he or she tends to feel more confident (McCaughey, 1998, p. 293).

In addition to taking a specific posture in order to feel better, emotions are also expressed by the body in order to indicate and communicate (to others) how the person feels.

Body Posture as Indicator of a Felt Emotion

In an experiment, Oosterwijk (2009) showed that people differed in body posture by sitting more straight or slouched in relation to words respectively related to pride and disappointment. This shows a direct relation between the felt emotion and changes in body posture.

Equally, body posture can also show a person's vulnerability. This vulnerability can be noted by possible attackers when a woman walks in a public space.(Foncke, 2012. p.22). In general, this is the one with the most insecure, vulnerable body posture. A study by Coulson (2004) illustrates how emotions are shown during certain postures. Figure 1 depicts the postures that are connected to fear. Fear is depicted by a slight slouch.

Figure 1. Postures connected to fear (Coulson 2004: p.124)

CASE: THE DESIGN OF A NECKLACE TO IMPROVE WOMEN'S FEELINGS OF PERSONAL SAFETY

In this case the particular focus on women was made based on the fact that women often have a lower safety perception in public spaces than men (Loukaitou-Sideris, 2005). In order to make women feel safer, several requirements are set.

Requirements

Based on the previously discussed findings it was concluded that if a person is walking slouched, he or she tends to feel less safe than when standing straight. The emotion that is experienced is also shown by the body, so when someone feels confident and stands up straight, this will be reflected in the body posture. The solution that had to be designed should, therefore, require the improvement of body posture by preventing slouching and provoking a straight posture.

In order to make someone feel more confident through an improved body posture, it is important to have something that reminds the person not to slouch. For the reminder to be effective while the person is in a public space, an important

requirement is that the reminder should not be obtrusive and that it be just-in-time (provide direct and real-time feedback to slouching behavior). This would require the solution to be able to detect current body posture (in order to react accordingly) and at the same time send a discrete signal to the person to provoke adjustment of posture if needed.

Solution

The start of the design iterations was to focus on the development of a necklace (as a possible fashion statement) that would detect body posture (through an integrated sensor) and would remind the wearer by releasing a scent (as non-obtrusive trigger) to change posture. Figure 2 illustrates the working principle of the necklace.

Figure 2: Working principle of the necklace

The Necklace as a Fashion Statement

As women wearing the necklace would probably want to be as inconspicuous as possible when walking around, the necklace should be either very neutral, or could in contrast make a fashion statement. The latter could have the additional effect of empowerment by feeling fashionable. Several designs were explored together with a fashion designer, in order to find the right balance between fashionability and the ability to integrate the needed technology. Figure 3 shows several explorations in the design.

Figure 3: Several explorations in the design of the necklace

Scent as an Associative Stimulus and Trigger

Scent was used as a trigger. Scent is non obtrusive and has the ability to work as an associative stimulus (Robin, 1999). For example, a certain scent can be associated to a place or experience, which in turn evokes a comfortable feeling. In addition, research also shows that liking and disliking of scents are both very personal and culture-dependent (e.g. Herz, 2005). For instance the scent of root beer is experienced as pleasant in the United States, while in the United Kingdom it is associated with a disinfectant (Kaye, 2004, p.60).

Based on these insights, one of the decisions for the design was that it should be possible to personalize or choose the scents. This would make sure the user could choose a scent that would make her feel as comfortable as possible.

Prototype

For the final prototype of the necklace, several techniques were included to be able to make it functional according to the intended working principle as depicted in Figure 4. An ADXL sensor was placed in the back of the necklace, which, through calibration, can sense whether the user is slouching. An Arduino microcontroller was used to program the accelerometer to make the aroma come out when someone is slouching. The aroma is spread by a filament taken from a hacked e-cigarette, for the purpose of prototyping.

Detecting Body Posture

When the accelerometer gets tilted, the scent mechanism is triggered. This means that when the position is changed to a certain point on the x, y, and z axes, the scent comes out.

The difference between standing straight and slouching has to be calibrated by the wearer herself. First, she sits up straight and presses the button on the necklace to register the value of the sensor. Then she slouches and presses the button again. After registering two postures, the microcontroller compares the absolute values of the difference between the good posture angle value and the bad posture angle value of X, Y, Z. It chooses one axis from X, Y, Z, which has the biggest absolute value of the difference. If the absolute of the difference between the current angle of the chosen axis and the good posture value is bigger than the absolute of the difference between the current angle of the chosen axis and the bad posture value, it fires the filament and LED on the Arduino board and emits the scent.

Figure 4: Functionalities and technology of PosturAroma necklace

The Trigger as Reminder

In order to vaporize the specific aroma, a filament from an e-cigarette was hacked for the purpose of prototyping. The filament gets heated, which in turn heats the cloth that is drenched in e-liquid. When using the e-cigarette in the habitual way, smoke comes out, but after adjusting it there is only a small amount of smoke. The filament can be seen in Figure 5.

Final Design of the Necklace

The necklace consists of 3D printed cases, the mechanism and fabric. The 3D printed cases are used to keep the mechanism in the right place, as well as to protect it. This can be seen in Figure 6. A bright colored fabric is used to improve attractiveness of the design of the necklace, depicted in Figure 7.

USER TEST

A small-sized user test was performed in order to investigate the functionality and initial experience of users. Five female participants were given the necklace for 30 minutes. They were asked to wear it at the place they were sitting at that moment. In this case all participants were sitting behind a desk. After they wore it for half an hour, they were asked several questions related to the experience of wearing the necklace. The questions were:

- How often did you smell the scent?
- Did you sit up straight?
- Did you think about it while you were wearing it?
- Do you think the scent is a pleasant way to be reminded of standing up straight?
- Does it work properly?
- Would you wear it?
- Do you have any comments?

Figure 5. Battery connected to a filament from an e-cigarette

Figure 6. 3D printed cases that hold the mechanism

Figure 7. One of the designs of the necklace.

Results

All participants thought that scent was a pleasant way to be reminded of a bad body posture. It reminded the participants that they had to sit up straight, because the connection between scent and body posture was made. The participants felt that the mechanism was not working perfectly and that it should still be improved. They smelled the scent inconsistently, because they sometimes smelled it when they sat up straight. This can be due to the fact that there is a lack of control over the distribution of the scent. It can also be due to a delay, which means that the scent is released, but it takes time for it to travel to the user's nose.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

One of the strengths of the proposed concept is that it involves empowerment by a fashion statement. At the same time it shows that scent can be used as a non-obtrusive reminder of emotion-affecting body posture. There is also a possible effect of personalized scents on comfort, which is interesting for future research. The necklace is situated in a more preventive approach rather than a defensive one.

A benefit of using e-cigarette filaments is that it uses cartridges that are interchangeable, which in turn would make it possible for the user to choose her favorite scent. For safety and durability reasons, however, other technical options should also be explored.

It is still to be found out whether the concept is effective when used outside, as it has not yet been extensively tested in the user's real environment. More design iterations and technical optimization are necessary to develop the prototype of PosturAroma into a potential product. Optimization is necessary in technical aspects, durability, safety, range of available scents, size and design. Some concerns need to

be taken into account should the project be taken further, to tackle unwanted negative emotional effects. For instance: the effect of scent as a trigger could wane over time, or it could become unpleasant to be exposed to a certain scent too often or for too long. Secondly, the choice of personal scents such as perfumes is a very conscious decision for women. The risk of overruling this cosmetic choice could have a negative effect on the willingness to use such a device. Moreover, framing this idea in a way that could suggest a possible solution to unsafe situations is problematic. Although it can be argued that the necklace can have a positive contribution to the perception of safety, this might be undesirable or even misleading. Further testing has to show what the real life effects are for the perception of safety. It will very likely point out that it has beneficial effects for the feeling of self-confidence as this is strongly related to body language and posture. But it could turn out that results for the perception of safety are slighter than expected when used in a range of real life situations.

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DESIGN FOR HAPPINESS & SUSTAINABLE SOCIETIES

Carolina Escobar-Tello

Loughborough Design School, Loughborough University,
Loughborough, Leicestershire, LE11 3TU, United Kingdom

✉ M.C.Escobar-Tello@lboro.ac.uk,

ABSTRACT

Sustainable Design, Design for Happiness and Well-being, and Sustainable Consumption present good opportunities, with strong potential, to change the current situation, improve the world foundations, and build more sustainable lifestyles and happier societies; although their relationship has not yet been studied widely in a systematic way, there are already many indicators which show that we can live happily and more sustainably, with much less material items and less consumption (Veenhoven 2004, Abdallah *et al.*, 2012). Through understanding the way in which design and the designer can contribute in a holistic way to the above mentioned, the Design for Happiness framework (DfH) (Escobar-Tello 2011) proposes an innovative design approach, process and tool-kit to design a 'sustainable material culture' (sustainable products, services or systems) capable of contributing to shaping and promoting society towards happiness and sustainable lifestyles underpinned by sustainable economic foundations.

BACKGROUND ISSUES, WORKSHOP GOAL, AND APPROACH

The overarching foundations of our current world structure have led to a 'material-centred culture' where the *systems of belief and values* pivot around externalities such as materialism and money. In the majority of countries around the world, particularly in western and developed countries, this 'culture' has been designed and marketed in unsustainable ways inviting users to buy and discard products more frequently (i.e., designing for obsolescence; fast-track consumption; cradle-to-grave design). Unfortunately, increasing evidence suggests that although economic growth has been increasing for the past 60 years or so, happiness and well-being, environmental and social capital, and sustainable lifestyles have been declining (Jackson and McBride 2005, Amna Silim 2012, Abdallah *et al.*, 2012).

Sustainable Design, Design for Happiness and Well-being, and Sustainable Consumption present good opportunities, with strong potential, to change the current situation, improve the world foundations, and build more sustainable lifestyles and happier societies; although their relationship has not yet been studied widely in a systematic way, there are already many indicators which show that we can live happily and more sustainably, with much less material items and less consumption (Veenhoven 2004, Abdallah *et al.*, 2012). Through understanding the way in which design and the designer can

contribute in a holistic way to the abovementioned, the Design for Happiness framework (DfH) (Escobar-Tello 2011) proposes an innovative design approach, process and tool-kit to design a 'sustainable material culture' (sustainable products, services or systems) capable of contributing to shaping and promoting society towards happiness and sustainable lifestyles underpinned by sustainable economic foundations.

The results and analysis of the data gathered through the various workshops carried out so far, confirm that the DfH framework is successful in translating complex values (i.e., happiness, sustainable design, sustainable societies) into tangible design values, and hence bringing designers, as well as multidisciplinary agents, into an innovative design mind-set. More significantly, it is also a seed for building more sustainable societies where individuals lead sustainable lifestyles; essentially, for triggering societal systemic shifts and enabling a transition at a broad societal system level (Escobar-Tello 2014, expected publication).

Aim:

The aim of this workshop is therefore to offer its participants the opportunity to experience and apply the DfH framework. Throughout the workshop participants will have the opportunity to design products, services or systems (PSS) through the use of the DfH process and tool-kit, allowing them to embed the abovementioned complex values in their design proposals.

It will equip them with the skills to replicate such learning experience, and enable great potential for social innovation, driving sustainable change in business, organisations and society. Moreover, the workshop will add to the DfH research evidence portfolio, which so far has focused on developed economies (UK). This workshop seeks to provide further evidence of its value, application, and impact in cross-cultural environments, and highlight further implications for the design discipline.

Delivery:

The DfH is delivered through a co-design workshop setting providing an environment for its participants, ideally multidisciplinary agents, to design and create. Its process and tool-kit serve as a method to bring from a bottom up approach the characteristics and values of what is important and meaningful for people. Throughout its phases, the workshop participants will approach design from a different perspective. Collaborative design dialogues that support sustainable design innovation processes will result in systemic level changes (PSS) with high potential to contribute towards happiness and sustainable lifestyles as opposed to the restrictive product improvement level. Depending on the time available, the outcomes of the workshop will be at a stage where they can be tested in a 'real world' setting.

Followed by a presentation of the theory underpinning the DfH, the participants focus on the session's design brief (a burning issue/problematic relevant to the context of delivery [i.e. Colombia]), immerse in a series of collaborative dialogues and idea generation stages, and give way to a series of conceptual design proposals. This workshop's process follows five phases (Figure 1) and will be supported by the workshop's facilitator and the framework's tool-kit. Participants will work in small groups.

Intended number of attendees:

- Minimum 6
- Maximum 30

Length of the workshop:

- **Ideally** full day – 6 hours
- It can be accommodated to half-day too (3 hours)

Characteristics of the space/room needed to conduct the workshop:

- Open 'studio' space
- 'Round' tables that allow working in groups (4-5 people per group depending on number of attendees).
- Magnetic 'white' boards
- Computer or facilities to connect laptop.
- Screen projector; sound.
- Materials – A2 and A3 blank paper, markers.
- Website/blog

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Figure 1. Design for Happiness Workshop – Phases and Guiding Narrative (Escobar-Tello 2014)

PLAYFUL CITY JAM

Dr. Valentina Vezzani
Research Fellow, School of Design, University of Leeds (UK)
✉ texvv@leeds.ac.uk

Dr. Tang Tang
Lecturer in Sustainable Design, School of Design, University of Leeds (UK)
✉ T.X.Tang@leeds.ac.uk

Fabrizio Pierandrei
CEO of PACO Design Collaborative (IT)
✉ fabrizio@pacollaborative.com

BACKGROUND ISSUES

On the occasion of the 2014 “Design and Emotion” Conference, Dr. Vezzani and Dr. Tang, from the University of Leeds, will work with Fabrizio Pierandrei from PACO to organize a one-day (6 hours) workshop aimed at using design thinking as leverage to create a sustainable urban community in Medellín. It attempts to test a portable model to engage stakeholders in the use of Design Jams for the development of a sustainable community.

Playful City Jam calls for the participation of Medellín communities and local organizations to work creatively and collaboratively with practitioners and students from different design areas (i.e., design students and teachers with social sensibility, government workers, community groups involved with social innovation processes, etc.) to deliver multi-sectorial solutions to promoting a sense of community and individual engagement in urban sustainability.

This proposed workshop, which is part of an ongoing project led by Dr. Tang and Dr. Vezzani, focuses on developing a design-led model and tools to enable the active participation of both individuals and local communities in sustainable living and therefore enhance their sense of community¹.

Previous experiences of running both global and local design jams in Leeds (in partnership with PACO) have resulted in a

1 McMillan, D. and Chavis, D. M. (1986) *Sense of Community: a Definition and Theory*, *Journal of Community Psychology*, Vol. 14, pp. 6-21.

“prototype” for applying collaborative design in the improvement of community living. *Playful City Jam* will test the effectiveness of the “prototype” developed in enhancing creativity and supporting spontaneous design activities, aiding an interdisciplinary group to work together on problem identification, design ideation, prototyping and implementation.

WORKSHOP GOALS

Playful City Jam focuses on a Medellín urban community and the theme of sustainable lifestyle; in particular, the attendees will be asked to work in team on a particular challenge of Medellín. This challenge will be suggested by Medellín Ciudad Inteligente² and will be kept secret until the Jam kick-off.

The aim of the proposed workshop is threefold:

- To test and evaluate the effectiveness of using *Design Jams* to engage urban communities, local (administrative) organizations and designers to co-produce solutions to urban sustainability and community development;
- To test the level of public interest and engagement in a *Design Jam* and assess participant feedback, knowledge and the skills they acquire to act on the issues related to sustainability after the jam.

2 <http://mdeinteligente.co/estrategia/>

- To contribute to the development of a portable model that would enable local administrative bodies to engage local citizens, organizations and design practitioners in the dialogue on sustainable community development. The aim is to produce innovative ideas and solutions starting from needs, expectations and knowledge of citizens involved themselves in the urban community for the co-creation of social innovations of real value for individuals and communities.

APPROACH: A DESIGN JAM

Playful City Jam is a design jam, planned and implemented by two organizations, by bringing different interests, resources and approaches together:

School of Design, University of Leeds (UK), represented by Dr. Tang and Dr. Vezzani, leading the study on sustainable design education and collaborative design. Co-organizers of the Global Sustainability and Service Jams³ in Leeds.

PACO Design Collaborative; a non-profit association for social promotion located in Milan (Italy), as an international network of holistic professionals and organizations, who believe in the potential of design and education to foster social innovation, sustainable behaviors and business opportunities. PACO is the local organizer of the Global Sustainability, Service, and Gov Jams in Milan. <http://pacollaborative.com>

Medellín Ciudad Inteligente; a program of the Medellín Mayorality and UNE EPM Telecomunicaciones (Colombia) that works on open government, citizen participation, social innovation, and sustainability. Its aim is to improve the quality of life of citizens through digital inclusion as well as citizens' empowerment and engagement. <http://estrategia.medellin.co>

The *Playful City Jam* aims to involve and activate different types of stakeholders who will co-produce tangible design outcomes on Medellín's real challenges. It is based on collaboration, sharing, inclusion, experimentation and fun. These characteristics will allow the attendees in Medellín to overcome their social and cultural barriers, to engage in discussions and understand common problems, to learn from one another, and to transform their ideas into a concrete design or plan of action which can become real.

The *Playful City Jam* will be based on the direct participation of:

- One of the Organizers: as coordinator and observer of all the activities along the jam;
- Jammers: working in team; at least one of them will be a designer;
- Facilitators: preferably designers who will be able to facilitate the dialogue within each team and the use of the tools provided, to give insights and tips during each phase of the jam;

3 To know more about the Global Jams visit: <http://planet.globalservicejam.org/content/about> and <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLjJM-jp5eYYXIEcDJsABfhO4zYhkqe2fC>

- Mentors: invited speakers who are familiar with the topics proposed at the jam. They do not have to be there all day, but should talk to every team and attend their final presentations.

The *Playful City Jam* will be structured according to the following phases and activities:

1. Welcome: the organizer will present the goals and schedule of the jam, and introduce the staff as support of the activities; mentors will be invited to provide quick insights and tips on Medellín's challenge suggested by Medellín Ciudad Inteligente) to be developed during the jam.
2. Warm-up: a game will be proposed to the attendees (including facilitators and mentors) to break the barriers among people and prepare them for teamwork.
3. Brainstorming and exploration: with the support of facilitators, jammers will cluster in teams and start to research and discuss the proposed challenge, starting from their experiences and interests.
4. Sharing ideas: each team will make a quick presentation of its own theme, ideas, and approach to overcome challenge. To allow teams to compare their processes and bounce off ideas to each other, they could share what they have done in the interim presentation before the lunch break.
5. Coffee/Lunch break: this phase will allow the teams to have a break, change focus, and continue the dialogue in and across teams.
6. Designing the idea: the teams will be provided with service design tools to support the development and communication of their idea, including a business canvas, and create prototypes, as tangible evidences of what to be implemented.
7. Final presentations: each team will present its own project, and a final discussion on the experience will be opened

During the jam, some activities and short interviews will be recorded by a video camera. Questionnaires will be used to assess attendees' expectations, personal interests, and feedbacks on the process and tools provided. Semi-structured interviews will be conducted to gather feedback from attendees on their engagement in the activities.

CONCLUSION / FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

The Playful City Jam in Medellín is an opportunity for the School of Design, Leeds University and PACO Design Collaborative to strengthen the collaboration with Medellín Ciudad Inteligente. It will open a way to further international longer-term projects on collaborative design for sustainability and social innovation.

Moreover, the workshop outcomes will be disseminated through the publication of academic journals.

Characteristics of the space/room needed to conduct the workshop

The space with moving tables and chairs should allow people to move easily, considering the planned activities. In particular, each team (from 3 to 6 people per each) will need a desk, chairs and ideally wall space.

- Space to project kick-off slides and video clips
- WiFi: stable and fast connection for all attendees.
- Coffee breaks: a room with enough space to create an area for coffee break and “relax”.
- Lunch break: preferably in another space (maybe outdoors) to allow attendees to change their focus, enjoy the social meeting and strengthen relations. If not a refreshment service in another place, a take-away would be an alternative.

Materials and special requirements

Movable tables (for working in teams) and chairs; projector; WiFi; stationery such as paper (A3 and/or A2), sticky notes, markers, scissors, tape, glue, cardboard.

Video camera with tripod and memory card to film some of the workshop activities and short interviews.

Refreshments: coffee, tea, juices, snacks and preferably also some sandwiches for the lunch break.

Communication of the event

The Playful City Jam event will have visibility online through the Playful School Project web page, hosted by the School of Design, University of Leeds website. Moreover, PACO and Medellín Ciudad Inteligente will promote the event on their own websites.

We will set up a project blog that will record the workshop, e.g., procedures and status updates, and a Twitter and Facebook page that will promote the event and involve the attendees before, during and after the Playful City Jam experience.

DIBUJANDO LA POBREZA, COLOREAMOS LA PAZ

Natalia Currea Dereser
Agencia Nacional para la Superación de la Pobreza Extrema

Carolina Ávila
100% Open

Mariana Amatullo
Art Center College of Design

Francisco Jose Noguera
Compartamos con Colombia

Ignacio Vidal
Socialab

We aim to motivate assistants to question themselves about the connections between poverty and peace in the Colombian context, and what poverty and peace mean to them as individuals and as a group. We feel that if we focus on how poverty and peace feel, the outcomes might be extraordinary.

WORKSHOP POSITION PAPER - BACKGROUND ISSUES

Poverty and inequality figures remain

“Colombia’s social agenda has undergone a dramatic evolution in recent years. The growth and sophistication of public social programs has been accompanied by a deepening of private sector involvement with poverty-related issues. However, poverty and inequality figures remain unacceptably high, and it is now accepted that neither sector’s offer is sufficient to create inclusion and address problems of poverty at the scale that is required. In this context, social innovation has been recognized as a tool that can unlock more effective approaches to issues of poverty, and facilitate the cooperation between actors in various sectors”.

The Agency and its Center for Social Innovation have been consistently working on discovering new ways and initiatives to

- 1 Taken from the Project abstract PIONEROS SYSTEM OF SOCIAL INNOVATION, presented to the Multilateral Investment Fund MINF in 2012, and approved in March 2013. Developed by Compartamos con Colombia in association with Anspe.

solve challenges related to poverty, viewing it from the potential of communities to create better solutions. Simultaneously, Colombia is going through a peace process that is fundamental for overcoming extreme poverty, as overcoming extreme poverty is fundamental for the success of the peace process. We see that people and organizations are talking about poverty and peace, but not experimenting how peace and poverty feel like. No time is being invested in imagining a different reality.

We want to develop a process in which participants can connect to what poverty and peace represent to them, and let them realize that the created process is really conducted by them, although facilitated by an expert.

WORKSHOP POSITION - PAPER- WORKSHOP GOAL

To develop a collective process of creation in which participants will come up with an idea (project) related to poverty and peace, so that it can later be developed by one (or more than one) of the leaders of the workshop.

WORKSHOP POSITION PAPER - APPROACH

Our approach is not theoretical but emotional. This means that the creative process will not be based on concepts or theories but on a set of questions that connect the participants to what they are going to create. In other words, we are going to focus on the “why” and not on the “what”.

NAMES, AFFILIATIONS AND CONTACT INFORMATION

The workshop is led by the Center for Social Innovation (CIS) of The National Agency to Overcome Extreme Poverty in Colombia (ANSPE by its Spanish initials) in collaboration with:

Art Center College of Design - Mariana Amatullo mariana.amatullo@artcenter.edu

100% Open - Carolina Ávila- caroavi@gmail.com

Compartamos con Colombia - Francisco Noguera francisco_noguera@compartamos.org

Socialab - Ignacio Vidal ividal@socialab.com

Center for Social Innovation-ANSPE Natalia Currea Dereser natalia.currea@anspe.gov.co

Fundación Bolívar Davivienda: Fernando Cortés fernando.cortes@segurosbolivar.com

Number of participants (Attendees): between 15 and 40, ideally.

Duration of the workshop: 6 hours.

Location: Bogotá D.C., Universidad de los Andes.

Target

The workshop is intended for multi-sectorial participants interested in comprehending poverty and peace from a different perspective, and willing to think and create collectively around these matters.

- Students (particularly on the areas of design).
- Professionals.
- Private sector.
- Public sector.
- Academia.
- Community.
- NOG's.

Characteristics of the Space

Taking into account the methodology and activities (collaborative work), the room should ideally have:

- Capacity for 80 people.
- Good illumination (natural light if possible).
- Movable structures (tables, seats)
- Structures that allow facilitators to post light elements so the creative process can be visualized by participants.

Materials and Special Requirements

Round tables seating 8 to 10 people (movable); acrylic boards and erasable markers; 15 to 40 seats (easily movable); post-its; sheets of paper; video beam; sound system.

LANGUAGE OF CONFLICTS: AN INTRODUCTION TO USING CONCERN CONFLICTS AS A DESIGN OPPORTUNITY

Deger Ozkaramanli, Elif Özcan, Pieter Desmet

ABSTRACT

This workshop is based on the proposition that concern conflicts can be powerful starting points for user-centered design processes. Concern conflicts arise when the user wants to simultaneously fulfill two concerns that require mutually exclusive choice alternatives. Imagine your alarm clock ringing in the morning. You need to attend an early morning meeting that is important for your work (concern for competence), but you also want to stay in bed to relax for as long as you can since you could not get enough sleep (concern for relaxation). What do you do? This is a typical example of an experience that involves a concern conflict, i.e. a dilemma. Dilemmas are pervasive in everyday life, and thus, they are a crucial part of every design context. The way designers formulate and address users' dilemmas can lead to creation of different product identities ranging from user-friendly products to products that promote social responsibility. In this workshop, participants will have the opportunity to explore different types of dilemmas and to create design concepts using new design tools and techniques.

INTRODUCTION

Designers are skillful in identifying and designing for unfulfilled wants and needs of their users: this is the premise of user-centered design. However, people pursue multiple and often conflicting goals during their everyday activities: we may decide to skip our gym-night to go to the movies (concern for entertainment), and yet, wish we would have a fine-looking body like the movie stars we admire (concern for beauty). Or we may want to show our best selves to increase our chance for a promotion (concern for competence), yet we also want to remain modest because we do not like to be perceived as being arrogant (concern for social approval). Designers can take any of these concerns as the starting point for designing something that appeals to the user. However, addressing unfulfilled concerns separately might result in designs that fulfill only one concern while ignoring the other. As a result,

these designs might evoke both pleasant and unpleasant user experiences. Therefore, we propose that focusing on the tension between the concerns, rather than on specific concerns in isolation, lead to solutions that tackle this emotional duality.

Users experience different types of dilemmas ranging from concrete and context-specific dilemmas (e.g. *I want to cook my own dinner versus I want to keep my kitchen clean*) to abstract and ideological dilemmas (e.g. *I want to be socially responsible versus I want to lead a comfortable life*). As a result, it is important for designers to be equipped with the knowledge and tools that support identifying and designing with users' dilemmas. In this workshop, the participants will be introduced to three main stages of a conflict-driven design approach that can support designers in designing with dilemmas (see Figure 1). The main challenges and opportunities of adopting a conflict-driven design approach will be discussed and future research directions will be identified.

Figure 1. Conflict-driven design approach

Stage 1 - Capturing Users' Dilemmas

An important challenge in the proposed approach is that it requires identifying users' dilemmas that are relevant to the user and inspiring to the designer. To address this challenge, the participants will be introduced to several research methods and gain hands-on experience with a work-in-progress research tool (i.e. co-exploration) developed by the authors.

Stage 2 - Formulating Relevant and Inspiring Concern Conflicts

Dilemmas are composed of two concerns that conflict each other in a specific design context. These concern conflicts can be taken as a starting point for design activities. As a result, the second challenge in the proposed approach is to distill concern conflicts from users' dilemmas and to formulate these concern conflicts in a relevant and inspiring way. For this, the participants will be introduced to various ways concern conflicts can be formulated based on the work of Desmet (2008), and Desmet and Ozkaramanli (2012).

Stage 3 - Developing a Design Vision for Addressing the Selected Concern Conflict

Identifying dilemmas and formulating concern conflicts take designers only half way through the design process. Therefore, the third challenge in the conflict-driven design approach is to generate design ideas that can address the concern conflict at hand. For this, the participants will be introduced to three main design directions (taking a firm stance, taking a flexible stance, or taking no stance) and supporting design strategies to deal with the concern conflicts they selected.

WORKSHOP

The goal of this workshop is to introduce a preliminary approach to conflict-driven design. The research questions we aim to address can be formulated as (1) what are possible criteria to select an inspiring dilemma? (2) What are possible criteria when formulating an inspiring and informative concern conflict? (3) What are possible criteria that designers use when forming a design vision to address a selected concern conflict? We welcome critical discussion on the usefulness of adopting a conflict-driven design approach and seek out inspiring tools to support its implementation.

Approach

Participants will be introduced to various tools and techniques that can support the implementation of the proposed design approach. The workshop will be composed of three 30-minute lectures followed by interactive exercises and reflective discussions. At the end of the workshop, designers will gain a comprehensive overview of tools and techniques they can use to implement the three main stages of the conflict-driven design approach.

TIME SLOT	ACTIVITY
09:30 - 10:00	Ice breaking session Present your 'dilemma'
10:00-10:30 (30min)	Lecture 1 - Introduction to conflict-driven design - Introduction to dilemmas and their main components - Defining the role of design in dilemmas - Exploring tools and techniques for capturing dilemmas
10:30 - 10:45	Morning break
10:45 - 11:45 (1hr)	Exercise 1 - Identifying inspiring dilemmas using co-exploration (in groups of 3-5 people) - Capturing dilemmas experienced in a specific design context
11:45 - 12:00	Discussion and reflection
12:00 - 13:00	Working lunch
13:00 - 13:30 (30min)	Lecture 2 - Distilling concern conflicts from users' dilemmas - Introduction to three levels and dimensions of concerns - Formulating concern conflicts within and across different levels and dimensions of concerns
13:30 - 14:30 (1hr)	Exercise 2 - Formulating inspiring concern conflicts (in groups of 3-5 people) Distilling concern conflicts from dilemmas Formulating inspiring and informative concern conflicts
14:30 - 14:45	Discussion and reflection
14:45 - 15:15 (30min)	Lecture 3 - Forming a design vision on concern conflicts - Introduction to three design directions and supporting design strategies that can be used to address concern conflicts
15:15 - 15:30	Afternoon break
15:30 - 16:30 (1hr)	Exercise 3 - Forming a design vision on concern conflicts (in groups of 3-5 people) - Using the design directions and design strategies to generate design ideas for addressing a selected concern conflicts
16:30 - 17:00	Group presentations of workshop results
17:00 - 17:30 (30min)	Debate on how to implement insights in design practice - Discuss key-insights - Discuss implementation in design practice

Workshop details - This workshop is intended to be a full day (6 hours) workshop. The number of attendees is between 12 and 15 people maximum. The organizers have no preference over the location of the workshop.

Requested materials - Wireless internet access, LCD projector and screen, name badges, flip chart, post-it sticky notes, A3 paper, writing pads, pencils, colour markers, colour papers.

Contact person - Deger Ozkaramanli, MSc., Delft University of Technology, d.ozkaramanli@tudelft.nl

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Ozkaramanli, D., & Desmet, P. M. A. (2012). I Know I Shouldn't yet I did it Again! Emotion-driven Design as a Means to Subjective Wellbeing. *International Journal of Design*, Vol. 6, Issue 1, 27-39.

SUBTHEME 2 Theoretical Issues of Design and Emotion

Relationships between the philosophical and theoretical foundations of human emotions and design.

Includes these topics:

- Philosophical and Theoretical Foundations
- Aesthetics and Emotion
- Desires, Motivations and Values
- Space and Time
- Situation and Context

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TIMELESSNESS IN SUSTAINABLE PRODUCT DESIGN

Alex Lobos

Department of Industrial Design, Rochester Institute of Technology

✉ Alex.Lobos@rit.edu

ABSTRACT

Shorter product lifespan driven by reduced durability and planned obsolescence is causing severe environmental issues and diminishing user experience. Sustainable Design is addressing this problem with strategies that improve a product's lifecycle and address important areas of impact in manufacturing, use, and end of life. This article explores how the concept of 'timelessness' can be used as an effective strategy for creating products that are cherished and enjoyed by their users, last longer, are easier to repair, and have better options for end-of-life. A series of case studies found in commercial products, as well as in student projects, illustrate how timelessness can be achieved at four levels: appearance, product efficiency, material selection, and user experience. Timelessness integrates sustainability and user experience in a natural way that is needed for elevating the quality of design and its impact on society.

KEYWORDS: *sustainability, design, timeless, emotion, education.*

INTRODUCTION

Industry growth allows for products to be developed and distributed at a fast pace. While this allows for easier accessibility to the latest technology and opens doors for multiple product selection, it also reduces the lifespan of products and diminishes their relevance in consumer's minds (Lobos & Babbitt, 2013). By knowing that there is a wide selection of newer — and in many cases cheaper — products out there, consumers replace them without thought or guilt. With this short lifespan comes a series of environmental and social consequences that cannot be ignored (Papanek, 2009; Tang & Bhamra, 2009). Products need to be developed with attention to their whole lifecycle in order to improve their manufacturing, distribution, useful life, and end of life.

Timelessness, a quality of not being affected by time, can be a successful way of extending product lifespan by protecting them from style trends and ever-changing consumer tastes. While discussions over timelessness cover in great detail aesthetic considerations of artifacts and their cultural relevance, this paper intends to drive the concept of timelessness beyond theoretical realms of appearance and culture and apply it in design practice as a tool for obtaining a sustainable advantage in product design. This advantage relies on creating products that have a universal language that remains current for a long time, paired with durability and dependability. The benefits of timelessness go beyond aesthetic considerations; they focus on creating something useful, and letting form enhance util-

ity and usability with as few elements as needed (Morrison, 2002). The result is a product that is meaningful for longer and allows for reparability and graceful aging. These factors help in offsetting any environmental effort put into producing the product and extending the product lifespan in a manner that elevates user experience and satisfaction.

PRODUCT LIFESPAN IN TODAY'S SOCIETY

Today's society looks at product lifespan as part of a short-lived cycle where artifacts are underused and quickly replaced by newer versions that promise higher performance at lower costs. Products that follow this model are the result of planned obsolescence: a strategy that makes useful goods be perceived as useless and outdated regardless of their functionality (London, 1932). Planned obsolescence has become a pillar for most economical models to the point where many countries' economical growth is measured on how much their population spends on goods and services (Packard, 2011). This model encourages society to produce and discard products as quickly as possible and is more common in western societies, whereas in eastern cultures the idea of purchasing something only once is more prevalent (Chapman, 2005). The economical incentive of planned obsolescence is complemented with a human instinct of turning possessions into symbols of who their users are, and who they want to become (Schultz et al., 1989). As people go through an endless cycle of outgrowing

themselves and wanting to become something different than what they are, they keep changing their material possessions, which ultimately leads to a consumerism pattern with negative environmental consequences (Chapman, 2009). Manufacturing processes consume large amounts of energy, water, and other natural resources in order to extract and process materials as well as to run infrastructure. The speed at which these resources are being used is far larger than their renewal rate, leading to an unsustainable pattern (Leonard, 2010). Also, the push for cheaper products compromises quality and makes products fail early. Since these products are manufactured as cheaply as possible, they are often impossible to repair or upgrade. The result is an unmanageable volume of trash that affects the environment and takes up precious space in the form of landfills or informal waste grounds. This cycle also diminishes the experience that users have with their products, leading to unsatisfied consumers that don't find products meaningful or relevant, and replace them without much thought or care (Hamilton, 2004).

SUSTAINABILITY IN PRODUCT DESIGN

Reacting to this negative trend in today's economy, sustainable product design has evolved as an important approach to product development, addressing issues created by outdated processes and behaviors. Sustainability strives for the implementation of systems that can meet today's needs without preventing future generations from meeting theirs (Hofstetter & Madjar, 2003). In order to achieve this, designers and engineers must develop products that optimize processes throughout their entire lifecycle. Frequent solutions include enabling material extraction and manufacturing with reduced energy requirements, simplifying transportation and packaging, prolonging product use, and improving end of life by reuse and recycling (Petrina, 2000). Nonetheless, true sustainability goes beyond ecological considerations and looks at broader issues that also address society and commerce, achieving solutions that are better for the environment, while also providing an improved and equitable quality of life (Fuad-Luke, 2007). In making a product's life cycle more sustainable, it is key to reduce the use of resources while assuring their future availability, all without compromising other stages or the quality of output. Many products use such high amounts of energy in their creation that the chance of this energy being offset during their useful life is unlikely. Another stage in the life cycle where there is significant room for improvement is end of life. From the consumer's side, end of life has high importance as it is up to most consumers to make sure that reduction of waste, reuse and recycling take place.

A typical approach for addressing energy-intensive manufacturing is to identify processes that are more efficient. This can be obtained by looking at materials, processes or both (McDonough & Braungart, 2002). While this strategy makes sense in terms of reducing environmental impact of products, it is only a partial solution. A deeper issue related to manufactur-

ing has to do with the ever-growing scale of products being produced, and the fast speed at which they are disposed of and replaced. Reasons for this trend can be low-cost (due to high volume of production), reduced durability (due to poor quality issues) or desire to acquire the latest product (due to marketing pressure). This tendency, commonly referred to as planned obsolescence, is imposing enormous pressure on our natural resources and making our way of life unsustainable.

TIMELESSNESS AND DESIGN

A product whose quality has been optimized has the potential to last the equivalent to multiple lifespans of comparable products. Reducing frequent product replacement can be achieved as long as a product is able to maintain its relevance to the user, both in terms of functionality and appearance (Lobos, 2011). Functionality in this case implies not only that the product will work for a long period of time but also that the product is easy to repair or upgrade. Appearance relates to an aesthetic that does not go out of style quickly. Achieving a long-lasting appearance can be the result of having a unique style, or, on the contrary, having as little ornament as possible. In both scenarios, products are able to disconnect themselves from popular aesthetic queues that will act as time and cultural stamps on them (Loos, 1908), and eventually make them be perceived as obsolete. The ultimate goal is then to achieve a superb performance and enhanced user experience that remains valuable to users time after time (Eisenstein, 2011; Mugge et al., 2009; Van Hinte, 2004).

Timelessness is an important design strategy that can lead to a successful extension of a product's life span. This is true in products that have been around for a number of years and that have become part of everyday life, sometimes throughout different cultures around the world. American manufacturer KitchenAid, for example, is best known for their iconic stand mixer (Figure 1). First introduced in 1919, the company released their classic Model K in the early 1930s, which has been trademarked and remains virtually unchanged since (Lidwell & Manacsa, 2009). The mixer's design has changed so little throughout the years, and design historian Victoria

Figure 1. KitchenAid Stand Mixer Model K

By Amy (Flickr: Behold!) [CC-BY-SA-2.0 (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/2.0/>)], via Wikimedia Commons. http://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/1/1a/Green_Apple_KitchenAid.jpg

Matranga (1997, p.150) describes how ‘every attachment in the stand mixer, for example—from the rotor slicer/shredder to the sausage stuffer—will work with every KitchenAid stand mixer ever manufactured, including the 1919 original Model H’. KitchenAid’s stand mixer offers a perfect integration of form, function, and aesthetics, and it is a staple in many kitchens around the globe. In 1997, the San Francisco Museum of Modern Art included KitchenAid’s mixer as one of only three items in its exhibition ‘Icons: Magnets of Meaning’ (Evans & Cullen, 2003), making it evident that this product is a true icon of American design.

Another example of timelessness in the industry comes from the German company Braun. During the 1960’s Braun developed multiple products that applied a simple, clean, and understated design language. These products, designed by Dieter Rams and his team, are an excellent integration of functionality, logic, elegance and convenience. Rams’ Ten Commandments of Good Design emphasize how design needs to be useful, durable, honest, and environmentally friendly, among other things (Rams, 2009). These guidelines are evident in products such as the SK-4 radio and record player (circa 1956), and its follow up models SK-5 and SK-6 (Figure 2).

The SK-4’s unique approach to product design lies in its ‘honesty’ and focus on function, clean of any ornament, and a clear order in the operating elements (Franksen et al., 1980). Another great example of Braun’s simplistic approach to design is the series of radios T3, TP1, TP2 (circa 1958), and T4 (circa 1969). These pocket receivers show little use of color and touch-points, and highlight the speakers with holes creating geometrical patterns with no desire of hiding their function (Ueki-Polet & Klemp, 2009). These radios are considered design icons, and it has been argued that they served as inspiration for the Apple’s popular iPod, introduced to the market in 2001, more than thirty years later (Linzmayr, 2004).

Ram’s philosophy on design shows a high degree of humility as he describes products, such as household appliances, as ‘humble servants, to be seen and heard as little as possible’. (Lovell et al., 2011). His principles are also used every day by designers that want to create products that are not described simply as ‘stuff’, but rather as important components of a person’s material landscape. Ram’s approach of creating not only simple designs but also better products might look simple in practice but it is extremely challenging to achieve, with an evident connection between form and function.

Good, responsible design shows a clear connection between products and their function, user and environment. Sometimes designers create forms for aesthetic pleasure only, but great designs always have in mind the situation in which they will exist. Masato Sasaki (2007) talks about how ‘good’ shapes cannot exist in isolation of function, and design is about developing answers to specific situations, not about creating forms. Sasaki’s commentary on good design is part of a reflection on Japanese designer Naoto Fukasawa, an important figure of modern design and responsible for a wide array of products, including a CD player for Japanese manufacturer MUJI (Figure 3). This design was first developed as a concept for the company’s ‘Without Thought’ exhibition in 1998, and it consists of a minimal wall-mounted CD player operated by simply pulling off a cord (Fukasawa, 2007). The concept was so well received in the exhibition that it was released to the market in 1999 and it’s still in production today.

MUJI is a Japanese manufacturer of household goods, founded in 1980. The company was conceived as a critique to the overload of low-priced products with poor quality out in the market, offering high-quality artifacts at very low prices. MUJI, which stands for ‘no brand’ in Japanese, has the purpose of ‘restoring a vision of products that are actually useful for the customer and maintain an ideal of the proper balance between living and the objects that make it possible’ (Kanai,

Figure 2. Braun SK-6 radio and record player.
By xavax (Own work) [Public domain], via Wikimedia Commons.
<http://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/0/04/Braun-Sk61.jpg>

Figure 3. MUJI wall-mounted compact disc player.
By Myself (Myself) [Public domain], via Wikimedia Commons.
http://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/3/37/Muji_NYC_inside_CD_players.jpg

Figure 4: REX peeler by Alfred Neweczarsal for Zena, Switzerland.

By Peter Wiegel (Own work) [GFDL (<http://www.gnu.org/copyleft/fdl.html>), CC-BY-SA-3.0 (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/3.0/>) or CC-BY-SA-2.5-2.0-1.0 (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/2.5-2.0-1.0/>)], via Wikimedia Commons http://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/3/3e/Sparschaeler_Rex_Star.jpg

Figure 5: Moka Express coffeemaker by Bialetti, Italy.

By photograph by Hans Chr. R., derivative work by Saibo (Own work) [CC-BY-SA-3.0 (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/3.0/>)], via Wikimedia Commons http://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/c/cd/Moka_Express_sideview.png

Figure 6: A set of "Akari" lamps by Isamu Noguchi.

By User Fluffy nns on ja.wikipedia [Public domain], via Wikimedia Commons <http://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/9/90/Ja-isamunoguchi-akariri.jpg>

2010 p.14). Following on this minimalist and timeless type of design, Naoto Fukasawa, along with British designer Jasper Morrison, organized an exhibit in 2006 entitled 'Super Normal'. The exhibit gathers a wide variety of products, ranging from anonymous everyday objects to design classics by Enzo Mari, Marc Newson, Isamu Noguchi and Achille Castiglioni, among others. All the products included in the exhibit share the same quality that Fukasawa and Morrison (2007, p.100) describe as 'something that's good to have around, that you use in a completely satisfactory way without having to think about its shape or decipher any hidden message or trickiness'. Some products included in the exhibit are Alfred Neweczarsai's REX peeler for Zena (Figure 4), Bialetti's Moka Express stovetop coffeemaker (Figure 5), and Isamu Noguchi's 'Akari' ceiling lamp (Figure 6). There is a peculiar balance in the Super Normal philosophy, in which old and anonymous objects are just as — or perhaps more — recognizable than recent designs from some of today's most famous designers, all sharing a common use of minimalism and simplicity.

Designing a product with enough opportunities to extend its life is not enough; there also needs to be a conscious effort to transform user behavior and to encourage the desire to keep the product for longer. Designers are able to steer consumers in specific directions in terms of purchasing, using, and disposing of products (Jelsma & Knot, 2002). The degree in which behavior can be affected ranges from subtle approaches that enlighten and spur desired attitudes to features that actively steer and even force specific behaviors (Lidman & Rendstrom, 2011). The effect of using physical characteristics of a design to influence function is commonly referred to as 'affordance' and it creates a very important bond between the signals that an object projects and how users perceive them (Gibson, 1977). Affordances are quite effective in making a product more intuitive and enjoyable, while avoiding

unintended use or abuse (Lidwell et al., 2010), and in the case of sustainability they can make a dramatic difference in assuring that a product will have a good, long lifespan that offsets the resources used for its creation.

APPLYING TIMELESSNESS IN PRODUCT DESIGN EDUCATION

In order for designers to effectively integrate timelessness into their design process, it is critical to expose them to this approach as early in their careers as possible. The goal of this exposure is for them to develop a set of tools that leads to meaningful products and also addresses sustainability issues. A perfect environment for introducing sustainability in design is in higher education, since it is during this time when designers develop their processes and skillsets, and unfortunately sustainability has not received the attention it needs in the design curriculum (Spangenberg et al., 2002). A series of courses on sustainable design at Rochester Institute of Technology's Industrial Design department are exploring topics such as emotional attachment, material selection, and timeless design, in order to improve product sustainability and encourage a longer, more meaningful lifespan. While the influence of time in design has been explored as a general philosophy and framework (Khoury, 2013), this educational effort is moving from a theoretical analysis and applying timelessness as a practical set of strategies for product design practice. The focus of these student projects is influenced heavily by Fukasawa and Morrison's concept of Super Normal, encouraging students to maximize simplicity and to create products so ordinary that they become extraordinary. Along with the notion of Super Normal, students explore emotional attachment as a catalyst for user experience. Products that

bond deeply with their users often turn from plain artifacts into bridges that connect users with other people, enjoyable experiences, and their overall environment. The implications of emotional attachment are important for sustainability, since products with these attributes have longer lifespans.

The product categories covered by these assignments are apparently simple: everyday products that exist in most home and office environments, such as tape dispensers, staplers, salt and pepper shakers, measuring cups, bottle openers and mortar and pestle sets. These products depend on simple technologies and mechanisms, allowing students to keep their attention on the subtleties of the products themselves rather than the technology that makes them work. But there are a couple of additional aspects that come with working on these types of products. One is of familiarity: most people use these products on a daily basis and because of this, students need to find a design approach that feels natural and intuitive. The second aspect is how to understand complexity within simple products. A good example of this discovery is in tape dispensers. Most students begin working on how to hold the tape in place and to develop an interesting shape around it. Very soon they realize challenging details, such as the dispenser's cutting blade: its complexity doesn't come from tearing the tape itself, but rather from the force used to pull the roll and to assure that the roll will remain extended and accessible when it's time for cutting the next piece. Other similar examples are finding the right shape and angle for the mouth of a bottle opener that will hold and open a cap effortlessly every single time, or the right angle and thickness of a measuring cup's spout, so that liquids come out right, preventing liquids from dragging and leaking.

ACHIEVING TIMELESSNESS FROM FOUR ANGLES

As students develop their products, they break down timelessness into four strategies that integrate functional and aesthetic elements: appearance, product efficiency, material selection, and user experience. As students explore these strategies they understand that each product has a different set of needs and opportunities, and that the best result will come from knowing how and when to combine different degrees of sustainable strategies. This multi-level approach is crucial in successfully addressing planned obsolescence given that product replacement is not necessarily the result of a single product deficiency, but rather the combination of several factors that accumulate over time (Van Ness & Cramer, 2003).

Appearance

This strategy is based on the notion that good design never goes out of style. Famous conceptual artist Syd Mead (2013), best known for the designs in iconic films such as *Blade Runner*, *Tron*, and *Mission: Impossible 3*, talks about how good design needs to be 'future-proof', meaning that it should avoid becoming outdated. For students, their goal is to de-

Figure 7. Mortar & pestle set by Joshua Rivers. Photo by M. Komeijani.

velop products with an appearance so simple and classic that it is hard for anyone to know if the products have been designed recently or if they have been around for a long time. If this strategy is successful, these products will have a better chance of being used for a long time and maybe even handed down to future generations.

Joshua Rivers' mortar and pestle sets use shapes that are simple, elegant, and engaging (Figure 7). Human factors play a big role in making sure that the products feel 'just right' in hands of the user, from proportions to shape to even weight. Models were created using rapid prototyping as well as aluminum sand casting, combining state-of-the-art technology with traditional manufacturing processes.

Product efficiency

Design is nowadays an additive process. In order to offer competitive advantages, products are filled with features and customized options. In most cases, these additions do not add significant value to products but compromise performance and dependability. Products developed for timelessness use an opposite approach that removes anything superfluous. As concepts are refined, there is a conscious effort of having each iteration being simpler, which means stripping away unnecessary components, shapes, parts, processes, and interaction. The goal is to bring products down to their most basic form and function. The result not only offers smarter products, but also reduces complexity during manufacturing in terms of the number of parts, assembly, etc. The simplicity of components also makes it easier for products to be repaired and optimizes lifespan (Khoury, 2013).

A tape dispenser by Robert Fish is created out of a single piece of sheet metal, using basic processes like bending, pressing and cutting in order to create functional details without compromising usability and appearance (Figure 8). Interesting details are the bumps on the sides that help to hold the tape in place while also providing more structure to the metal, and the pattern in the front edge of the piece that serves as a cutter to tear off and hold the tape. The overall style of the dispenser consciously leaves a rough finish and slight blemishes in the metal to add personality and the perception of longevity to the product, borrowing from 'Wabi-sabi', a Japanese

Figure 8: tape dispenser by Robert Fish. Photo by M. Komeijani.

Figure 9: Salt & pepper shakers by Chen Guo. Photo by M.Komeijani.

Figure 10: Bottle opener by Bridget Sheehan. Photo by A.Lobos

concept that celebrates aesthetic imperfections as symbols of natural beauty that enhance simplicity, modesty, and intimacy (Koren, 1994).

Materials selection

Materials are a key factor in product design. Their choice will drive many decisions, not only in terms of manufacturing but also in terms of weight, durability, finish and appearance, recyclability, etc. In terms of sustainability, material selection needs to balance energy used for extraction and manufacturing with durability during use and potential for recyclability. It is also preferred to minimize additional processes such as painting and texturing. For their projects, students focused on wood, metal, glass and ceramics, as these materials are durable, easy to manufacture, and can age gracefully. The final designs celebrate the materials chosen by turning them into a focal point of the design. For some of the designs, students analyzed how material choice impacts the product's environmental performance. After creating CAD models of their design, students used Autodesk's Inventor Eco-Materials Adviser (EMA) plug-in to assign two different materials and compare them side-by-side in aspects such as cost, transportation, embedded energy, durability potential, etc. EMA was extremely useful to students in determining which material offered the best environmental advantage, and then connecting that information with notions of perceived value and physical appearance.

Chen Guo's set of salt and pepper shakers uses a simple shape with an inner compartment for holding condiments (Figure 9). The design is versatile enough that it can be produced out of wood, plastic or ceramic. After analyzing the environmental

impact of each material, Guo proposed plastic is a good option for high-volume productions, and wood for shorter runs. EMA also made evident that for the wooden version, eliminating chemically based finish coatings improved environmental performance while enhancing wood's natural beauty.

User experience

Emotional Design is an approach that goes beyond form and function and addresses the experiential elements that happen whenever using design solutions. The benefits of emotional design offer important benefits to the user, as products designed under this philosophy are more engaging, authentic and easier to use (Desmet & Hekkert, 2009). Patrick Jordan (2000) talks about how in order to reach an emotional level products need to achieve three levels of experience. First, they need to be functional, or in other words, to solve a need. Second, they need to be usable so that users know how to interact with them and accomplish their tasks. Third, products need to provide joy and pleasure when used. It is important to understand that Jordan's theory assumes that product pleasure can only happen after functionality and usability have been met. Good design then involves having strong attention to detail without losing sight of how a product comes together and provides a meaningful interaction beyond the sum of its parts.

Bridget Sheehan's bottle opener shows an understated form factor that is intuitive to hold and to use (Figure 10). Sheehan's choice for an apparently simple object allowed her to spend plenty of time considering design details such as the right length, width, thickness, and finish. The opening that

grips the bottle top was tweaked several times to make sure it would open different types of caps. There is a satisfying aspect about holding and using this bottle opener given its proportions and sturdiness, and the stainless steel should age gracefully as marks of wear begin to appear.

CONCLUSIONS

One of sustainability's largest challenges is the continued urge to replace products that are still functional. This challenge, in big part blamed on planned obsolescence, is leading to an unnecessary accumulation of products with lower quality and with appearance that goes out of style quickly and in a predetermined pattern. This issue is of particular interest to product designers, given that they are the ones that determine the appearance and experience of objects. Creating timeless products is an effective strategy for prolonging the lifecycle of any product. When users acquire artifacts with strong functional, aesthetic, and experiential attributes, they connect at a stronger level with them and use them for longer. Products designed under this approach can also be designed for reparability, upgradability, and recyclability, increasing their sustainability benefits even further.

In the development of timeless products, it is important to understand trade-offs as a key element of sustainable design. A common example is the use of better materials, which can lead to higher cost. In this case, manufacturers need to make evident to consumers that a higher initial cost is an investment and will most likely pay itself off with a longer useful life and higher product satisfaction. In other cases, however, higher product quality does not imply a more expensive product. Companies such as MUJI have defined business models that allow them to offer products with superior design and quality at the same price points as competitors. In this case, timelessness not only provides a competitive advantage at the time of purchase, but it also allows for production lines to require minimal changes over time, increasing manufacturing efficiency and offsetting investment costs dramatically.

An excellent way to measure the success of a product is by observing how it withstands the passing of time as good designs maintain popularity regardless of trends and consumers' ever-changing tastes. Timelessness provides strategies that make products less likely to become outdated or easily replaced. The case studies illustrated earlier highlight how timelessness can be used effectively to elevate the perceived value of a product and to extend its lifespan beyond plain functionality. Timelessness creates a strong connection with users and it can be described as something that gets better with age. This approach is essential for any designer's tool kit, and that's why it's important to integrate it not only in design practice but also in education. The student projects described in this article demonstrate various approaches for students to integrate timelessness attributes into their designs in an effective and elegant way. Designers are interested in developing design solutions that are long lasting and engaging, and timelessness is a perfect vehicle for achieving

this connection and to offer solutions that defy traditional expectations for product lifespan and for user satisfaction.

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THE EFFECTS OF CONTEXT IN PRODUCT COLOR TESTING

Bryan Howell
Brigham Young University, Provo Utah, USA
✉ bryan.howell@byu.edu
Estefania Marin
Universidad EAFIT, Medellin, Colombia
✉ emarina@eafit.edu.co

SooJeong Kook
Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology
(KAIST), Daejeon, South Korea
✉ kookwp1@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This paper introduces insights into color exploration and testing methods that designers and marketers should understand in their efforts to accurately define appropriate color choices for future products.

The paper combines two independently conducted color research surveys that demonstrate how individual color preferences easily change when viewed in three different contexts. First when they are viewed as a stand-alone swatch of color, second when they are viewed on a product itself, and third when products are viewed on alternative colored backgrounds. These surveys were designed and conducted by guest researchers at Delft University of Technology.

This paper also reviews typical product color exploration methods involving color trend services, color semiotics, and traditional color wheel based aesthetic rules and explains that, although insightful, these methods are not as effective in identifying individual product color preferences as context is.

KEYWORDS: *color preference, design and marketing, product color, background color, color management.*

INTRODUCTION

Color has influenced consumers in various areas for a long time, including fashion, product manufacturing, and brand development. One of the reasons that color is such a crucial element in design is that it possesses the potential to influence a consumer's purchase by generating an emotional satisfaction or association that is meaningful to the consumer. The fact that companies such as Nike, Apple, and Christian Louboutin expend substantial resources to develop, market, and protect their color strategies, demonstrates the importance and power of effective color strategies in business (Singh, 2006; and Westland, 2013).

For example, Nike's bright yellow 'Volt' color is currently virtually synonymous with the Nike brand itself, since it is incorporated into many of the products that constitute the Nike range. Furthermore, Apple computer has required purchasers of their new iPhone 5c to select a product from a family of colors that conspicuously lacks the traditional dark grey or black color. In Christian Louboutin's case, they have trademarked their 'red sole' on high-end women's shoes and have recently garnered international news headlines regarding their arduous legal battle with their competitor, Yves Saint Laurent, over the use of red soled shoes (Buchart, 2013).

These examples demonstrate the importance of, and a commitment to, product color in marketing efforts.

Generally, a color marketing strategy includes both the management of existing and future color properties as well as information regarding individual and familial color development and application to a product line and brand in order to make a profit. Applying 'any' color does not guarantee successful sales in the market. Thus, designers and marketers should be concerned with methods that will aid them in uncovering 'appropriate' colors for their products.

One of the researchers involved in this paper has significant personal experiences in defining product color palettes for a number of Fortune 500 companies. His experience shows that color decision makers often rely on the 'art' of color selection to make product color decisions. This art consists of mixing personal experience and historical product category traditions with insights from color semiotics and the psychological associations that humans make with colors, knowledge of traditional color wheel rules such as complementary and analogous color schemes, and subscriptions to color trend providers whose job it is to predict what colors are going to be popular in the market during the coming year. When a palette of potential color is selected, these color choices are then tested through a customer verification

process or, at least, an Executive Review, which authorizes final selections.

The verifying of color preferences with users typically occurs in either a live focus group involving various color samples or using a web-based survey tool. Both scenarios allow users to consider and select which colors they prefer, thus providing the decision makers with the confidence that a robust process has been followed and that the 'right' colors have been identified.

However, two independent studies involving color preference selections have shown that user preferences for colors are easily changed based on the context that the colors are tested in. Context will be defined in this paper as the situation, environment, layout, or scenario in which color preferences are tested.

These studies demonstrate how three different contexts provide three different color preferences from users. The first context involves a stand-alone color swatch tested independently from the market category. The second context introduces the product category into the color test, and the third context changes the color of the background surface on which the product's color is tested. The result being that with each change of context, color preference also changes.

This paper argues that color decision makers need to be aware that the simple testing of color preference with people or online is not as robust as instinctively imagined. Users are easily swayed by the context in which colors are tested. Incorporating this knowledge into future color exploration and testing will increase the accuracy of color test efforts as well as increase confidence in the process that leads to the final product color selections.

COLOR TREND

Color decision makers often hire color trend consultants such as Natural Color System (NCS) or subscribe to color forecasting organizations like the International Color Marketing Group. These companies and associations are committed to investigating worldwide color trends and sources with the expectation that their knowledge and insight will provide decision makers with the necessary knowledge to make appropriate color decisions.

Data points, styles, and insights for these services are derived from various sources such as the fashion industry, architecture, music, and emerging cultural phenomenon from around the world. Based on their findings and publications, designers create inspirational color and material boards which visualize how and why certain colors should be incorporated into the final product. For example, figure one shows a color and trim board used to inform the final color for the K16 electric motorcycle.

Although these color trend sources are insightful, they are primarily starting points to begin the color exploration, which will lead to final product color specifications.

Figure 1. Color and Trim inspiration boards used to convey future color trend predictions for the K16 Electric Motorcycle.

Contrary to the argument of this paper, they freely mash contexts together to enhance the narrative they are developing. As demonstrated in the examples in figure one, the designers provide contextless color squares, which hint to a mix of product categories such as transportation, furniture and fashion. They also manipulate backgrounds to white or grey to demonstrate emerging trends. Yes, these types of exercises provide general insight into current color trends, but they provide little regarding absolute user color preferences within the product's context.

COLOR SEMIOTICS

Another common method of product color exploration used by decision makers involves color semiotics or the psychological and cognitive meanings associated with colors. Stephen Westland (2013) argues that color communicates meaning and concepts through associations and can evoke emotional responses from viewers.

For example, figure two shows various red images that each convey a different meaning through association. The red rose typically symbolizes love or passion, the red-cross equates with health care and emergency aid. The red stop sign is commonly used around the world to control traffic, while the collection of red hearts indicates a 'cute' love or valentines day. Finally, the red card is symbolic of stop, danger, and the ultimate penalty and removal from the game.

Figure 2. Examples of how the color red is associated with different meanings. For example the rose reflects passion and love, but the small red card equals stop, danger, and penalty.

Figure 3. Red colors can also be associated with brands. Can you identify which hue belongs with Coca-Cola and which with Netflix?

Another example of color associations or semiotics involves brands. Figure three shows two different red squares, one is from the Coca-Cola logo and the other from the Netflix logo. Are consumers able to identify which color associates with which company? Yes, and consequently, brand colors are legally defensible as demonstrated by the lawsuit between Christian Louboutin and Yves Saint Laurent. The color on the left hand side of the page is Coca-Cola, the color on the right side is Netflix.

Color semiotics strongly influence consumer behavior. Studies show that customers quickly make decisions subconsciously, even before they think and compare options or features. The associations between color and connotations are made during early stages of visual processing as a key mechanism for quick decision-making and survival (Labrecque & Milne, 2011).

These associations are made by the acquisitions of memories. The memory trace (Buzan & Buzan, 2000) comes from the creation of connections between neurons that represent associated stimuli. Perception of products comes from memories or the relationship among emotions and colors. Consequently, people tend to choose colors they associate with

emotions that are meaningful to them, for example, yellow and cheerful (Labrecque & Milne, 2011).

The associations of colors and emotions are also directly connected with the visceral state of the person at the time of choice (Lee et al., 2011). The visceral level of product perception is the relationship between the impact of the appearance and the emotions evoked from a product that is related directly with the consumer's cultural background.

The semiotics of colors can be used in various ways in product design, and designers should understand the basics of the principles and incorporate them in color explorations. However, the meanings people associate with colors vary depending on things like culture, religion, and regional traditions; they are neither consistent nor predictable. Although understanding the issues surrounding the notion of color semiotics is important, it is not a robust method to identify consumers' final product color preferences.

COLOR WHEEL HARMONY RULES

Another way to explore families of potential product colors is to use traditional 'color wheel' based theories. A 'color wheel' is the range of colors in a circular spectrum that shows relationships between different visible colors. It was developed three hundred years ago and has been used as a foundation for a variety of color theories ever since (Westland, 2013).

There are several schematic color groups that are known to be effective in color theories. Johannes Itten (1961) promotes in his book *The Art of Color* such combinations as, triad, analogous, and compound schemes. He further explains these to be rules that artists can use to provide an aesthetic appreciation regarding colors.

Nowadays, digital web-based color wheel tools such as Adobe Kuler (2014), as shown in figure four, have been invented and used by many designers and marketers to aid in color family development. The color tool's meticulous calculations quickly provide numerical and visual results for a number of classic color scheme rules and allows users to create new schemes of their own.

Figure 4. The web based Adobe Kuler Program incorporates the traditional color wheel to both visualize and quickly explore a variety of color rules. The image on the left displays an Analogous color rule while the image on the right displays a Triad based color rule.

Although this tool is fun to use and provides respectable and quick predefined color relationships, it is limited in its ability to aid color decision makers to accurately test perception of a product's color. Primarily, this tool allows designers to explore color relationships and to numerically define color specifications.

COLOR PREFERENCES

A number of studies have been done related to color preferences in humans. They typically test color preferences in a contextless situation. Other studies demonstrate that individual preferences will vary depending on the environmental colors applied in a retail situation. However, in regard to color preferences on products, there are few research articles to review.

For example, Holmes & Buchanan (1984) teach us that color preference of an object cannot be found independently of the object. Another example is Saito's (1983) work which found color preference changed when measured with and without a context.

Stephen Palmer from the department of Psychology at the University of California at Berkeley has performed a number of such studies, including one on 'Object Color Preferences' that was recently published in April of 2012. From this study, Experiment Three is of particular note to this paper. This experiment indicates that there is no difference in color preferences between imagined, depicted and actual objects. Palmer's recommendation is challenged by the findings presented in this paper, which argue that context, the situation, environment, layout, or the scenario in which color preferences are tested makes a significant impact on color preference.

INDEPENDENTLY RUN COLOR RESEARCH SURVEYS

With these notions of context in mind and to aid in understanding the affects of color preferences in and out of context, tests from two different researchers were performed and analyzed. Because the tests were performed independently from each other, the data sets are not perfectly aligned, and one includes information on proportion that is not necessarily critical to this paper's position. However, in general both tests contribute substantially to the paper's position.

TEST 1: THE "CONTEXTLESS" COLOR SWATCH TEST

In this study, a questionnaire on color preferences was created and invigilated using online methods. A selection of twelve colored squares or swatches were chosen to obtain a broad range of color choices, including black and white. The respondents were between the ages of 19 and 35, from European, American and Asian cultural backgrounds with the ratio between male and female at 1:1.2, or roughly evenly distributed.

Figure 5. These are the contextless color swatch samples used to obtain preferred and not-preferred color choices from respondents.

Figure 6. Results for preferred and not-preferred contextless color preference study.

Participants were asked to pick a color they liked and one they disliked from 12 color squares presented to them on a white background as shown in figure five. Participants were not provided or requested to imagine a context for the colors, they were simply asked to identify their personal 'preferred' and 'non-preferred' colors. This sets a foundation from which to demonstrate how color preferences can vary in follow-on tests and exposes respondents to the notion of personal color preferences.

Results of the "Contextless" color swatch test

The results of the test show that the majority of participants liked a blue-tone color such as cyan #7 and blue #8 from the figure above. There appears to be no noticeable preference differences based on the respondent's culture backgrounds. Many respondents disliked the orange #4, green #6, and brown #11 colors. See figure six below for the overall results.

These findings basically align with those proposed in Palmer and Schloss's (2010) Ecological Valence Theory. This theory proposes that people prefer colors that are associated with positive experiences, such as the color blue associated with blue skies, and dislike those colors associated with negative experiences like rotting vegetation and excrement such as dark browns and yellows.

TEST 2: THE COLOR "IN CONTEXT" TEST

In test two, both a product category and form were added and considered by respondents in their color preference selections. A collection of the ten most recent Apple iPhones were used as colored objects in order to test color preference. The iPhone's original colors were not modified in any

Figure 7. Images of the ten Apple iPhone colors used to provide context for the color preference test.

Figure 8. These charts show the 'most' preferred and 'least' preferred colors results from testing with an iPhone providing the context.

way. However, a material change from metal to plastic occurs between the first group of five phones, numbers one to five, and the second group of five phones, numbers six to ten. This change in material and texture could have an impact on the color preference but was not explored in these tests. The iPhone color samples are shown in Figure seven below.

The respondents were asked to perform a series of color selection exercises involving the neutral colors and the metallic colors and finally were asked to identify their 'most preferred' and 'least preferred' colors from all ten samples.

Results of the color 'in context' test

The results shown in figure eight below indicate that gold #4, silver #5 and space grey #3 colors are the most preferred, and that pink #7 is the least preferred. The survey also identifies gender color preferences as well, and although this separation is interesting and worth further study, it is not pursued in this paper's argument.

These findings show a significant difference from the findings in test one, which tested contextless colors. Whereas the palette of blue and pink colors were preferred 'out of context', when put 'in context', they did not perform nearly as well. In fact, the pinkish hue was the least preferred of all available colors in this particular context. Although the hues were not identical in the two tests, this demonstrates that providing a context causes identical respondents to alter their color preferences from previously measured contextless surveys. It would be advisable to further explore the effect of category on color preferences. For example, a test involving the same colors and textures, but changes in the category from mobile phones to another consumer electronic category, such as personal computers or home media players, might uncover how category affects color preference.

TEST 3: THE COLOR ON 'DIFFERENT BACK-GROUNDS' TEST

Test three examines how different colored backgrounds, employed when testing the color preference of objects, affects test subjects' color preference. A second researcher, not in direct collaboration with the first researcher mentioned in this paper but exploring a similar topic, performed this test. Consequently, the numbers of respondents and type of questions being asked are somewhat different than previously shown.

This test was performed using an online survey and included forty respondents between the ages of 18 and 28, from European, Central American, and Asian cultural backgrounds.

A collection of seven product attributes was selected against which to measure product perceptions. The attributes, created with input from peer Industrial Design researchers and insight provided from the writings of an online expert reviewer (Finnamore, 2013), are: elegant, classical, male, simple, dynamic, childish, and bright. The survey consisted of four different image sets of a green iPhone that had been manipulated to show four different color proportion combinations. These iPhone image sets were displayed on a white background in one scenario and a dark wood background in the second scenario. These two scenarios were then measured against the list of product attributes. For this paper, the proportion data from this study will not be further discussed. However, the product attribute data generated by the testing is directly applicable to our argument.

In the survey, respondents qualified each set of iPhones using the attribute list. They could only match one attribute with any one of the four image sets. In the first set of questions the green iPhone sets were displayed against a white background as shown in figure nine, below. Intuition suggests that this white colored background is neutral and will not influ-

Figure 9. iPhone sets on a white background, with corresponding attribute data. High scores are highlighted in green.

Figure 10. iPhone sets on a dark wood background, with corresponding attribute data. High scores are highlighted in green.

ence color preferences. Interestingly, it also simulates the typical white table found at Apple stores where products are displayed.

In the second set of questions the identical green iPhone sets were displayed against a dark wood background as shown in figure ten, below. Identical questions were asked in this second set of questions as in the first set of questions. Intuition, in this case, suggests that a simple background change should not alter the perceived qualities of a tested product.

Results of the color on 'different backgrounds' test

As can be seen in the two charts, the exact same iPhone sets received different attribute responses based only on differing backgrounds. Every response but one, the Male attribute in option four, changed in its perceived quality. Of the high scores, three of them, Male, Simple, and Childish, post a difference of 22% to 30%, while Dynamic and Bright show a 13% and 16% difference respectively. The remainder, Elegant and Classical show a 5% and 9% difference.

From this evidence it can be concluded that background choices influence perceived product attributes and consequently, could also influence product color preferences. It is interesting to speculate on why this occurred.

One researcher suggests that this phenomenon is similar to Johannes Itten's (1961) teaching on 'simultaneous color contrast'. He teaches that human eyes physiologically attempt to counter balance whatever color we are looking at with its complement. This effect cannot be photographed or observed outside of our minds. It is a natural physiological occurrence and causes us to perceive colors differently based on the environment in which the color is viewed. This theory provides an example of how a background can influence a product's color perception.

Another researcher suggests that changing the background from white to wood alters the values and associations regarding the material and intrinsic properties of the product. For instance, the green iPhone on a wood background could suggest an 'ecological' association, while a silky black textured background would convey a 'luxurious or sensual' association. These different associations affect intrinsic values in the respondents, which are then manifest in their preference selections.

CONCLUSION

Color selection for products is a difficult task at best. Color decision makers search for clear, simple and robust methods of color development and selection that provide appropriate, motivating, and convincing solutions to both internal development teams, and the end consumer.

This paper has demonstrated that evaluating color preferences in different contexts has an impact on respondents' color choices. Color swatches, when tested independently of the product prove to be highly misleading as a product color choice indicator. For example, the blue family proves to be the preferred color family when tested against other colors in a contextless environment. However, when similar colors are tested within a specific context, in this case mobile phones, color preferences change from blues to formal colors such as, gold, silver, and grey.

This paper also suggests that the background colors used behind a product are not inconsequential in color preference testing. The testing has shown that alternative backgrounds cause changes in attribute assignments related to colors. For example, the results of identical iPhone product sets tested on a dark wood background will not produce matching results when they are tested on a white background. The difference in the two scenarios is not insignificant and deserves further study as to why and how this occurs.

Finally, it can be argued that differing contexts, defined in this paper as the situation, environment, layout, or scenario in which color preferences are tested, clearly influence color preference among test respondents. Thus it becomes beneficial for designers, marketers, and other decision makers, to depend on more than their intuition in pursuing color choices. They need to understand and manage color choice through context in order to accurately develop and test product colors.

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LIFE-CYCLE INTERACTIONS FOR MODELLING HUMAN EMOTIONS

A FOUNDATION FOR DEVELOPING 'DESIGN FOR EMOTION' SUPPORT TOOLS

Jonathan C. Borg, Lawrence Farrugia
Concurrent Engineering Research Unit, University of Malta
✉ jonathan.borg@um.edu.mt, lawrence.farrugia.07@um.edu.mt

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a theoretical model representing human emotions as consequences of life-cycle interactions. Research into product design has been in the most part, limited to emotions elicited as a result of user-product interactions that take place during the use phase. Yet interactions involving humans, the artefact, and other life-phase systems span across the entire life cycle of the artefact. The study of emotions in product design should therefore be broadened by comprehensively considering and understanding the human interactions that occur across different life-phases. The implication is to consider human emotions, which result from the interactions involving the human worker, the artefact and other systems, as these take place throughout various life-cycle phases. The life-cycle interactions model, presented in this paper, establishes the foundation for the development and application of support tools, which take into consideration the influence of product design in eliciting emotions from human workers and customers.

KEYWORDS: *Meeting theory, life-phase systems, worker emotions, life-cycle consequences, CAD tools*

PROBLEM BACKGROUND

Research in product design and emotion has limited its focus on the study of emotions elicited as a result of the user-product interactions which take place during the use phase in the life-cycle of an artefact. In reality, the interactions between humans and the artefact are not exclusively limited to the use phase. Instead, throughout its life, the artefact interacts with multiple artificial and natural life-phase systems, where the latter includes human beings. It follows that human-product interactions take place throughout numerous life-cycle phases, which precede and follow the use phase. Some examples of interactions involving the artefact, the human worker, and other life-phase systems are: manual assembly of the evolving artefact during the manufacturing phase, the repair of a product during the servicing phase, and the disposal of a product by a human worker at the end of the artefact's life-cycle. These simple examples indicate that in order to understand the impact of product design on human emotions, one has to broaden the meaning of the term 'human-product interactions' in order to include both the end customer and life-phase human

workers. In this manner the understanding of emotions elicited as a result of human-product interactions will span across the entire life-cycle of the artefact.

Over the years, researchers have proposed numerous approaches that support designers in creating artefacts, which elicit positive emotions from the end customers, particularly during the use phase. Fenech and Borg proposed a phenomena model (Fenech & Borg, 2006a) of product emotion elicitation, which was subsequently used in the development of an approach (Fenech & Borg, 2006b), intended to provide design for emotion support. This approach was later implemented into a prototype design tool (Farrugia et al., 2008), which employs computer aided sketching in order to support the conceptual synthesis of a product form that elicits positive emotions.

A repertoire consisting of 25 emotion types (Desmet, 2012) was proposed due to the fact that previous emotion taxonomies were either too concise or extremely complex to be employed in design practice. In their research work, Fokkinga and Desmet (Fokkinga & Desmet, 2012; S. F. Fokkinga & Desmet, 2013) proposed a design approach whereby they demonstrated

how negative emotions can create emotionally rich product experiences for the users. In this paper the authors explain how under very specific conditions, people are willing to engage and enjoy activities which are known to elicit negative emotions, such as fear.

Ludden and Schifferstein (2009) investigated the influence of scents on the evaluation of a product by the end customer. A similar research work (Rahman, 2012) investigated the influence of visual and tactile stimuli on the end customer's evaluation of a pair of denim jeans. The investigation presented in this paper (Rahman, 2012) concluded that both visual and tactile stimuli can elicit sensations of different intensities, thus influencing the user's evaluation of the artefact.

The auditory sense is also a medium through which positive or negative emotions can be elicited. Fenko et al. (2011) investigated the impact of product noise on the user's experience. According to the authors, the definition of the term 'noise' should not be limited to the auditory property of a product; instead this term should include visual noise such as cluttered visual patterns. The study (Fenko et al., 2011) suggested that product noise resulting from visual patterns, had little influence on the participants' evaluation. On the contrary, the

auditory noise of a product had a negative influence on the overall pleasantness of the product as perceived by the evaluators. In view of these results, the research in this paper (Fenko et al., 2011) concludes that designers need to take into consideration the auditory characteristics of the product as this can influence its evaluation by the end customer.

The above state-of-the-art review pertaining to design and emotion, exclusively takes into account the emotions elicited by a product as a result of the interactions taking place during the use phase. Yet the use phase represents only one instance of the many phases in the life-cycle of a product (Olesen, 1992). Each life-phase may involve the interaction between the artefact, which exists in a certain state, the human being, and other life-phase systems, as illustrated in Figure 1.

The emphasis of this research, is that human emotions are not elicited exclusively from the human customer, but also from the life-phase worker_X, where 'X' corresponds to a distinct life-phase (1), (2), (3) and (4) shown in Figure 1. Research into product design and emotions should therefore extend to other life-cycle phases in order to include the emotions of human workers who interact with the evolving artefact throughout life-phases, which precede and follow the use phase.

Figure 1. Human interactions and the elicited emotions across the entire life-cycle of the artefact

The objective of this paper is to present a theoretical model for the emotion elicitation of both human workers and users, which stem as a consequence of life-phase interactions. The next section will provide a brief overview of the process involved in the elicitation of a human emotion and its influence on other aspects, such as physiology and behavior. The literature in this section will also outline why the knowledge pertaining to the elicitation of worker emotions is of relevance to the industry, thus providing a justification for the applicability of the model presented in this paper.

The third section of this paper will present the original theoretical model that has been adapted for the purpose of this research. The fourth section will present in detail the model for human emotions in life-cycle interactions, which is the main contribution of this research. This model presents human emotions as a result of interactions involving the artefact and some natural and/or artificial life-phase systems, as illustrated in Figure 1. During the manufacturing phase (1) a human worker executes the expected tasks by interacting with the evolving artefact and a life-phase system such as a drill press. The model portrays worker emotions as one of the consequences that stem from the interactions involving the worker, the artefact, and other life-phase systems. The value of making the knowledge embodied in this model explicit is that it would enable product designers to take into consideration the influence that product design commitments have on the emotions elicited from life-phase workers who interact with the evolving artefact and other life-phase systems.

This model is then used in the fifth section in order to provide a rationale for the results obtained from an investigation into worker emotions. A discussion pertaining to the results obtained from this study will be presented within the same section. The main conclusions of this research, together with the limitations and further work, are presented in the last section of the paper.

THE APPRAISAL PROCESS IN HUMAN EMOTIONS

The study of human emotions is a vast and growing area of research, particularly in the field of psychology. It has only been in recent years that researchers have started to understand and propose theories regarding the process pertaining to the elicitation of emotions in human beings. One of the most accepted and proven theories, pioneered by Richard Lazarus (2006; Lazarus, & Folkman, 1984), is called appraisal theory. According to Lazarus (2006) an emotion is the result of an appraisal/evaluation of the impact of a stimulus to one's own concerns. Scherer et al. (2001) propose the idea that specific appraisals elicit distinct emotions. Thus, for example, while an unexpected and motive consistent stimulus results in the elicitation of hope, an unexpected and motive inconsistent stimulus results in the elicitation of fear.

The appraisal process is only one aspect of an emotion prototype (Russell, 2009). This is due to the fact that an emotional event brings about a number of changes such as, bodily

changes (Russell, 2003), including changes in physiology (Michie, 2002; Scherer et al., 2001); vocal and facial expressions, together with changes in perception (Fokkinga & Desmet, 2012); attitude (Fokkinga & Desmet, 2012); and behavior (Michie, 2002; Yang & Diefendorff, 2009).

Yang and Diefendorff (Yang & Diefendorff, 2009) examined a theoretical model (Spector & Fox, 2002) originally proposed by Spector and Fox (2002). The principle idea behind this theoretical model (Spector & Fox, 2002) is that negative emotions elicited by environmental stimuli render individuals more susceptible to engage in counter-productive work behavior (CWB); both towards people within the organization and/or the organization itself. This costly CWB is engaged, sometimes unconsciously, with the intent to reduce negative emotions. The result of the investigation (Yang & Diefendorff, 2009) was in support of this theory.

Other studies (Chang & Lu, 2007; Imtiaz & Ahmad, n.d.; Jo, 1992) have investigated the impact that stimuli such as the spatial configuration (Michie, 2002), temperature (Jo, 1992), work overload (Qureshi et al.), and other characteristics pertaining to the work environment have on worker emotions and their behavior as a consequence.

The research presented in this section indicates that the elicitation of negative emotions from the life-phase worker, can result in costs being incurred as a result of reduced productivity, increase in absenteeism, and slower product development. This indicates that there are tangible and valuable benefits to industry in making knowledge concerning life-phase interactions, involving the human worker and the elicited emotions, explicit.

THE ARTEFACT AND LIFE-PHASE SYSTEM INTERACTIONS

During each distinct phase of its life, the artefact interacts/meets with a number of life-phase systems (Borg, 1999) such as the fabrication, assembly, and inspection systems during the manufacturing phase, and the disposal system during the disposal phase. The systems, with which the artefact meets, can be classified as being natural or artificial, as shown in Figure 2.

Material handling equipment, such as fork lifters and fabrication machinery, such as a drill press, are all examples of artificial life-phase systems, while the human being and the natural environment are instances of natural life-phase systems. While interacting with these life-phase systems the artefact, or rather some of its properties, are transformed from one state to another (Hubka & Eder, 1988). The type of transformation that takes place depends on the previous state of the artefact and the life-phase systems involved in the interaction (Borg, 1999)

The illustration in Figure 3 shows the artefact during the manufacturing phase (1) of its life. Throughout this particular phase, the artefact changes its state as a result of the interaction with other life-phase systems. Thus during fabrication (A),

the artefact changes its physical state from unperforated to perforated by interacting with an artificial life-phase system called a drill press. In a similar fashion, during assembly (B), the artefact interacts with an assembly system consisting of an industrial robot, which changes the state of the artefact from unassembled to assembled. Similarly, during inspection (C) the artefact interacts with an inspection system that identifies any potential fabrication and assembly defects. Following inspection the artefact changes its state from un-inspected to inspected.

HUMAN EMOTIONS IN LIFE-CYCLE INTERACTIONS (HELCI)

The meeting concept presented in the preceding section revolves around the notion that the artefact meets with various natural and artificial systems throughout its entire life. The changes which the artefact experiences depend on the previous state of the artefact and the attributes of the life-phase systems involved in the interaction. Apart from the artificial systems shown in Figure 3, the life-phase interactions involve the participation of human life-phase workers who contribute in changing the state of the artefact.

The diagram in Figure 4 illustrates the meeting/interaction involving the artefact, two artificial life-phase systems, and the human worker_M during the manufacturing phase. The human worker_M and the drill press interact with the artefact in state 'i', in the context of an artificial work environment. The interaction results in the transformation of the artefact from state 'i' to state 'i+1'. In addition, this interaction produces consequences including the generation of noise and waste. It should be noted that the type of consequences, and their respective attributes, depend on the properties of

the artefact and the life-phase systems involved in the interaction. For example, if during the manufacturing phase the artefact material is recyclable then the waste which is generated as a consequence of the manufacturing phase interaction may also be recycled.

The novelty of the model presented, is that an additional consequence that stems from the interaction involving the human worker, the evolving artefact, and other life-phase systems, is the elicitation of emotions. Like other consequences, such as the generation of waste, the emotions elicited depend upon the attributes of both the artefact and the other life-phase systems involved in the interaction.

In the context of the example shown in Figure 4, the change in the emotional state of the worker_M is in part determined by the properties of the artefact and life-phase systems involved. If the worker_M interacts with a drill press which is unreliable, then this interaction will result in a progressive change in the emotional state of worker_M from happy to angry. In a similar fashion, if the life-phase worker_M is performing tasks within a factory that is uncomfortable with inappropriate lighting, then these properties of the work environment will also contribute to a change in the emotional state of the human life-phase worker_M.

The concept behind this model may be extended to other phases in the life of an evolving artefact as illustrated in Figure 5. Each phase 'X' in the life cycle of an artefact involves the interaction between the life-phase worker_X, the artefact, and possibly some other natural and/or artificial life-phase system. These interactions will result in an intended change in the state of the artefact, together with a number of consequences, such as the generation of waste, noise, and pollutants. The emphasis of the HELCI model is that life-phase interactions will also produce a change in the emotional state

Figure 2. A classification of life-phase systems

Figure 3. The evolving artefact during the manufacturing phase

Figure 4. Worker emotions elicited as a consequence of manufacturing life-phase interactions

of the life-phase worker_X. For example, during the transport phase the use of reliable and efficient material handling equipment within a safe work environment contributes in changing the emotional state of worker_T from sad to happy. Similarly, during the disposal phase, the worker_D may become gradually sad due to work being performed using dangerous and hazardous equipment.

This section presented a model of human emotions in life-cycle interactions (HELCI), which portrays the change in the emotional state of life-phase human workers and customers as a consequence of life-cycle interactions involving the artefact and other life-phase systems. The change in the emotional state of the human workers and customers depends on the properties of the artefact as well as the other life-phase systems involved in the interaction.

CASE STUDY - WORKER EMOTIONS IN VISUAL INSPECTION

Semi-structured interviews among six factory operators were carried out within a manufacturing company. All of the

participants in this semi-structured interview, were workers who interact in a direct manner with the artefact by conducting visual inspections on assembled artefacts. These inspections are executed in order to identify any scratches or other cosmetic defects. This task entails the use of magnification equipment and powerful light sources in order to render the cosmetic defects easily identifiable. The aim of the investigation was to determine if the theoretical HELCI model provides a rationale to the emotions elicited in a realistic scenario. In addition, the investigation would enable the research to identify the attributes pertaining to the artefact and the other life-phase systems which are considered to possess an emotional quality.

Key results

Throughout the semi-structured interviews the participants identified various attributes pertaining to the artefact and life-phase systems which were deemed to be responsible for the elicitation of emotions. Table 1 provides a list of attributes pertaining to product, work, or process that were considered by the participants to influence their emotional state.

Figure 5. Human emotions in life-cycle interactions (HELCI)

TABLE 1. A SUMMARY OF THE RESULTS OBTAINED

Attribute	Comment	Number of participants (Percentage %)
Excessive ambient noise levels in the work environment	The constant exposure to loud noises emanating from machinery can be tedious and frustrating.	5 (83)
Product colors	The color of the product can facilitate or impede the task of visual inspection.	5 (83)
Physical layout of workers	Workers not provided with ample working space feel frustrated, particularly if this state has to be sustained over an extended period of time. Another issue was the provision of chairs which do not offer proper lumbar support.	4 (67)
Layout of non-human elements e.g. machines and WIP	The cluttering of the factory floor which renders the physical environment: a. Unappealing b. Potentially hazardous c. Impractical to work in.	4 (67)
Illumination provided for the process	The illumination is a critical resource necessary to execute the task of visual inspection. Without appropriate illumination the task would be very difficult.	3 (50)
Tactile feeling	The subjects prefer a certain product because of its tactile feeling.	3 (50)

Table 1. A summary of the results obtained

The most frequently mentioned attributes were the excessive ambient noise of the work environment and the product colors. Both the physical layout of workers and the layout of work in progress (WIP) material, were two attributes of the work environment that were also considered by 67% of the interviewees to have a significant impact on their emotional state. In addition, the provision of proper illumination for inspection and the tactile feeling were also deemed to have some influence in eliciting worker emotions. It should be noted that apart from the results shown in Table 1, there were other desirable characteristics pertaining to the product and other artificial life-phase systems, which were identified by a minority of the workers to influence their emotional state. Such characteristics include the colors of the physical environment, the aesthetic appeal of the artefact, and the overall reliability of the machines and tools being used to execute the expected tasks.

Discussion

Based on the responses from the sample of participants, the results indicate that characteristics identified to have a capacity in eliciting worker emotions, can in fact be attributed to the properties of the artefact and other life-phases systems, such as the work environment. However, a more significant outcome that stems from the investigation is that the elicited emotions are a consequence of the meeting/interaction involving the human worker with the artefact and/or other life-phase systems. This implies that HELCI is a suitable theoretical model for describing life-cycle interactions as the basis of eliciting human emotions.

A human emotion is characterized by the evaluation of a stimulus/event in relation to one’s own concerns. This explains why certain attributes, pertaining to the artefact, process,

or the environment life-phase systems, were considered to have a higher degree of influence in eliciting emotions when compared to others. The illustration in Figure 6 provides a very good example of how the same attribute of the artefact, such as color, is appraised quite differently from the life-phase worker when compared to the user, thus eliciting contrasting emotions from both humans.

With reference to Figure 6, the life-phase worker and the customer interact with the artefact during distinct phases of the product’s life, which in this case are denoted by the manufacturing phase (1), and the use phase (2). The illustration in Figure 6 shows that the life-phase worker interacts with various properties of the artefact, one of which is color. Both the life-phase worker (3) and the end customer (4) are interacting with the same identical color, yet the same product attribute is appraised very differently. On one hand the appraisal of the life-phase worker results in the elicitation of negative emotions such as anger (5). This is due to the fact that the particular choice of color impedes the ability of the human worker to conduct the task of visual inspection, which is a major concern to the worker. On the other hand the end-customer appraises (6) the same identical product attribute in a more positive manner, thus eliciting more positively toned emotions. This is due to the fact that the concerns of the end-customer are significantly different from those of the life-phase worker. The major concern of the customer is to have a product that is aesthetically pleasing, and in the example shown in Figure 6 the choice of color is beneficial in relation to this particular concern.

In a similar manner the provision of appropriate lighting during the manufacturing phase, can determine the extent to which positive or negative emotions are elicited from the life-phase

Figure 6. The appraisal of artefact's color by the life-phase worker and the customer

worker. The presence or absence of this resource can significantly influence the degree of difficulty in identifying cosmetic defects. The same rationale explains why excessive ambient noise was considered to play a major role in eliciting negative worker emotions. This is due to the fact that the exposure to constant excessive noise can quite often be distracting, hence detrimental to the task at hand.

Another example of an attribute related to the work environment that was considered to elicit negative emotions was the organization of the physical factory floor, which in most part was cluttered with boxes filled with WIP. The interviewed subjects pointed out that this attribute of the physical work environment elicits negative emotions due to the fact that it renders the execution of tasks more difficult. Thus, apart from being visually unpleasant, the existence of a cluttered work environment poses a threat to the execution of tasks by rendering the physical work environment impractical to work in, as it renders the flow of material for inspection very difficult.

It should be noted that a minority of the participants pointed out characteristics pertaining to the artefact, such as aesthetics and texture, as possessing a desirable emotional quality, thus eliciting positive emotions. The significance of this point is that while certain attributes are integrated into the product

to elicit positive emotions from the customer, the same attributes may also elicit similar emotions from the workers who interact with the product throughout other life-phases. This is particularly the case when a product attribute does not interfere with the concerns of the worker. Unlike the product color, the texture of the artefact was considered to elicit positive emotions due to the fact that it did not influence in any negative manner the execution of the required tasks.

CONCLUSION

For many years, research into product design and emotion has in most part focused on the notion that emotions are elicited from the human customer as he/she interacts with the designed product during the use phase. The research work presented in this paper extends this idea by taking into account the numerous interactions, involving the human worker, which occur throughout different phases in the life of an artefact. The state-of-the-art literature suggests that the elicitation of emotions from human workers can in fact have a significant influence on their behavior. Thus it would be appropriate if the design of a product could contribute in the elicitation of the desired emotions from both the customer and the life-phase worker.

The main contribution of this paper is in the provision of a theoretical model (HELCl), which portrays human emotions as a consequence of interactions, which occur across the various phases in the life of a product. These interactions involve the human worker, the artefact in its various states, and a number of life-phase systems. The HELCl model provides a basis for understanding the emotions, which stem from each interaction. This is due to the fact that at its core, HELCl links the characteristics of the artefact, and other life-phase systems, with the emotions that are elicited as a consequence of life-phase interactions.

This underlying principle of HELCl has been demonstrated through the results obtained from an investigation into worker emotions within a manufacturing company. The study identified characteristics which were considered to elicit worker emotions. The human emotions were elicited as a result of the appraisal of stimuli in relation to the concerns of the worker. It follows that the reason why particular characteristics can elicit emotions is that these can facilitate or interfere with the execution of the expected tasks. The investigation also shows that while certain design decisions, related to the product characteristics, are made in order to elicit positive emotions from the end customer, the same characteristics can elicit significantly different emotions from the worker.

Although this work has focused on human emotions in the manufacturing phase, the results indicate the need to carry out further research by considering interactions involving the human worker across other life-cycle phases of the artefact. A limitation of the research presented in this paper was the small number of workers who participated in the investigation. Apart from a larger sample size, it is deemed necessary to conduct additional semi-structured interviews among workers who are concerned with the execution of a diversity of tasks that are not necessarily limited to visual inspection.

The intent of this research in the near future will be to exploit the gathered knowledge by implementing a CAD tool. The starting point in the development of such a CAD tool is the HELCl model. To this extent the HELCl model provides the basis for the structuring and for rendering explicit knowledge related to the emotions elicited from human life-phase workers. The CAD tool could be implemented in order to support the design of products which can elicit the desired emotions through the interactions which occur across various phases in the life-cycle of the artefact. This will provide industry with a means of reducing the costs incurred as a consequence of negative emotions, which include counter-productive work behavior and an increase in absenteeism.

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EMOTIONAL AND RATIONAL ASPECTS OF THE MORPHOGENESIS OF MULTIMEDIA PRESENTATION

Anna Zyrianova

St.Petersburg Institute of TV, Business and Design, Russia

✉ makaranya@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

An approach to the creation of multimedia presentation is described in which presentation is considered as a rational/emotive, logical/imaginative and informatic/compositional formation. Primary attention is given to an artistic structure of the multimedia presentation, the prospects offered by its interactive potential, the interrelation of spatial and temporal organization with the logical organization of an interactive hypertext message, and the relationship between artistic and logical means of expression. Logical construction of multimedia is considered in a five-level system based on a synthesis of the research in the field of information architecture. The system levels are compared with the levels of compositional organization derived from the analysis of empirical material.

INTRODUCTION

Multimedia presentation

Presentation is a delivery of essential information about a person, organization, service, or idea in a logical and a visual form simultaneously. Multimedia presentation is a specific delivery, which is structured in an electronic hypertext multidimensional space and interactively developing in time on the two-dimensional screen. This definition is equally applied to the local and network editions (e.g. websites). As opposed to changeable web-based multimedia (such as a blog), multimedia presentation is a complete art form.

Multimedia presentation is a framework for storage, transmission, and delivery of information. Due to the integration of logical and imaginative expressive means, this form of message is likely to be the most effective. The present study of morphogenesis of multimedia presentation is an attempt to understand the laws that control the multilevel organization of an electronic publication turning it into an effective message.

Two aspects of perception: rational side and emotional side

Presentation is a kind of multimedia electronic publication, which is a document existing in a virtual environment. As a document, presentation bears informative, communicative, and cumulative functions (Bulatova, 2008). Each of these functions has both discursive and imaginative aspects. From

the discursive point of view, the text of the presentation should be constructed logically, conceptually, intelligibly, uniquely, and consistently. This kind of information is transmitted sequentially and is perceived by the person (i.e., the recipient, the addressee) from a rational standpoint. Shaped as artistic meaning the message of the presentation is constructed integrally and pictorially; it should be created as a completed picture of a 'model of reality' (and this model should be generated by the addressee) (Lotman, 2005). Artistic meaning of the message is transmitted throughout the structural modeling as a whole. Message takes the form of a sign, a symbol, 'an image that ... [is] perceived concurrently, simultaneously in all its parts' (Meshchaninov, 2008). This kind of information is transmitted instantly and perceived by the person (the recipient) from an emotional standpoint.

Thus, the logical side of information delivery is perceived rationally and the imaginative side is grasped emotionally. Cumulative implementation (synthesis) of discursive and imaginative communication determines the set of rational and emotional perception of the message. This creates a high degree of approximation of interpretation by the addressee of the information that has been sent him by the sender. Two pieces interwoven and shaped as artistic design creations produce one masterful end result.

Two communicating aspects operate on the principle of complementarity, holistically delivering the content in the form of a presentation. The holistic form of presentation is created in the synthesis of discursive and imaginative expression. We believe that in the case of directly integrated multimedia

communication, the holistic form is realized as a result of synthesis of an informational/programmatic organization and corresponding compositional organization.

Two aspects of forming messages in interactive multimedia: the informational/programmatic side and the compositional side

On the side of informational/programmatic organization, a logical structuring of the message data in hypertext is performed. On the side of compositional organization, an artistic structuring of messages in the virtual space-time environment is performed.

On the one hand, a scientific approach is applied to information structuring, but on the other hand, the artistic approach takes the lead.

Science and art are called ‘the two ways to explore the world’ (Lotman, 2005). One could compare them with ‘two eyes of human culture, the difference (and equality) of which create the bulk of our vision’. Let’s examine both points of view. We, scientists, examine the natural processes, and then organize congenital processes and repeatable phenomena. We, artists, explore the untravelled road and create an experience of both what had happened and what may or may not happen. A scientific way for the development of a multimedia presentation is to organize the data and the algorithms of interaction with the data by means of hypertext. An artistic way is to create a certain mythological-symbolic context in a multimedia virtual environment. An experience at any point in the study of this art is exactly the moment of understanding.

A virtual space-time environment allows one to use expressive means of spatial, temporal, and spatio-temporal, as well as synthetic forms, of art. However, it should be mentioned that the Russian researchers of multimedia (Demidova, 2006; Filippov, 2003; Jatsuk, 2009; Pakhomova, 1988; Shchitova, 2004), who recognize the audio-visual artistic nature of multimedia, place the visual aspect in first place. Moreover, as a matter of common knowledge, the American scientists have shown the following: a perceptual speed of information coming from reading or hearing, is only 100 bits / sec, while in the case of visual information this parameter reaches 200 million bits / sec (Light Feather & Aznar, 2011, p.36).

Thus, visual communication can be assessed as the most effective, and this fact informs the direction of our work, mainly in terms of visual means of expression.

Whereas the term ‘New media art’, which includes such genres as ‘Computer graphics’ and ‘Digital art’, etc., has already entered the dictionary, it was not until 2012 that multimedia presentation was considered as an art form developed according to its own canons. The author of the present work ‘generated awareness about a multimedia presentation as a new type of art’ (Adobe Design Achievement Awards Gallery, 2012, page number), and described the principles of its aesthetic organization (Zyrianova, 2011a), where the rational and emotional constituents combine.

For understanding the rational elements of user experience in web design and software development, Garrett’s model (‘Elements of User Experience’) has become a reference for web and interaction designers (Garrett, 2002). Surprisingly, this succinct diagram has proved to be useful for projecting decorative, performative, and media arts, and with certain modifications has been extended to the artistic means of expression and artistic patterns of organization, representing the ‘Elements of Viewer Experience’ (Modular Design Biennale, 2013; Zyrianova, 2011b, 2014). Merged together, the rational ‘User model’ of J. J. Garrett, and the emotional ‘Viewer model’ developed by the author revealed both general and specific laws of composition of multimedia presentation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Informational/programmatic organization

The information technology, abstract-logical, aspect of designing multimedia has been explored by Garrett (2002), Goto and Cotler (2004), Nielsen (2003), Rosenfeld and Morville (2002), and Phyo (2003). The authors demonstrate the rules of constructing a hypertext information space of the electronic publication and interactive user interface on the screen — in terms of science.

J. J. Garrett describes the process of website creation from the standpoint of the software interface and structuring the information space (hypertext system). Methodology largely affects the scientific side of design rather than the artistic. Garrett considers the process from idea to implementation of the project and highlights five levels of ‘user experience’ on it. The levels are mutually specified, wherein they are arranged in a certain sequence. The first level (1) is ‘strategy’, which sets the design goals and targets. The second (2) is ‘scope’ (both content and functional specifications), which selects the information units and the options for combining them. The third (3) is ‘structure’, which defines the information architecture and the interaction scenarios with the user. At ‘skeleton’ (4), the navigation (interaction logic) is developed, the interface (methods of interaction) is refined, and information design (structure) of the page is advanced. The upper (5) ‘surface’ compiles the information treated at the early levels and establishes sensory communication between the final product and the user. Schematically, the process of product formation is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Informational/programmatic organization suggested by J. J. Garrett

We consider this scheme as a basis for the abstract-logical aspect of designing a presentation. The particularity of the artistic organization forms of multimedia presentation led to particular modifications in the scheme of informational and programmatic (informatics) organization. The scheme has been modified in co-ordination with the works of Rosenfeld and of Phyo, as well as with the results of the experimental work of the author.

Considering the model of information and multimedia presentation software organization, we also distinguish five levels: (1) 'strategy', (2) 'scope', (3) 'hypertext structure', (4) 'navigation and interface', and (5) 'layout'. Unlike Garrett's model, this model separates the design logic and interaction methods (4) of the design structure of the page, moving the latter to a separate (5) level of organization (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Informational/programmatic organization in our edition

The fifth level of Garrett's scheme, the level of visual organization, in our work is brought beyond the information and software schemes and is fixed in the scheme of composite organization, as shown below. The other parts of the two models essentially coincide.

Our proposed model takes into account two aspects of hypertext interactive communication structuring: the hypertext system and the software interface (informational and programmatic). Figure 3 shows that the 'scope', on the information side, includes the content, whereas on the program side it incorporates the options for the program content links. The 'hypertext structure' deals with information architecture and interaction design. At the next level, the navigation within the information space and the software interface interaction take place. The information and software components are linked at all levels in the layout and are presented to the user in the publication.

Figure 3. Two aspects of informational/programmatic organization

Compositional organization

In order to explore the artistic side of the organization, we turned to the fundamental works of Lotman (2005) and Kagan (1972). Lotman claims that art is essentially a simulation activity. Art creates an analogue of reality — an artwork. An artwork is created in a certain system, in its characteristic form of expression, and using a characteristic artistic language. This means that an artwork is realized as a certain material substance. Kagan states that an artwork arises, appears, and presents itself to the viewer as a material design: as a conjugation of the colour patches, volumes, sounds, words, and movements.

Based on the form of expression, Kagan classified art into three groups: plastic (or space), spatio-temporal, and temporal art. He especially highlights a fourth group: synthetic skills combining the features of the three major groups. Web design technology allows one to use a variety of information media: text, graphics, photos, 3D graphics, video, animation, sound, and telecommunications. Information can be submitted in the form of appropriate arts: literary works, planar images, three-dimensional graphics, video narration or animation narration, music and voice tracking. Thus, the electronic form of expressive means can handle a wide range of arts and can work as a synthetic form of art.

An electronic form as an art form was first discussed in 1993 when, after a visit to Silicon Valley in California, the artists John Heemskerck and Dirk Paesmans created the website *jodi.org*. The site was positioned as 'the website-as-an-art-work' (Tribe & Jana, 2006). The artists followed the example of the Dadaists who were manufacturing collages from magazine clippings. For the collages a variety of electronic images and html-codes, sliced and mixed, were used. Widget messages in this symbiosis acquired a new meaning and artistic expression, which, in this case of preventing the perception of the initial information, carried new artistic information: about the irrationality of Dada philosophy.

The authors of the site *jodi.org* have mainly aimed at graphic means of expression. Aside from the graphic language, artistic information in multimedia can be transmitted by means of the literary language, the language of exposition design, and cinematography.

An electronic presentation, or site, can be regarded as spatial art when we pay attention to the graphical design of the page, and to the way in which the information is structured in the virtual space (information architecture), as a durable and spatial-durable one when we observe a step-by-step variation of audio and video content of the screen. It is, however, a special novel form which offers a variation of plot lines and screen contents owing to a special novel technique: interactivity.

How can one compose all these tools in one system? We do this by correlating, in other words, by drawing parallels between the spectrum of artistic means of expression, and the means of informational/programmatic organization of multimedia presentation.

DRAWING PARALLELS

Multimedia presentation provides the possibility of combining various types of art form into a single form. A multimedia product creates an analogue of reality in several systems simultaneously. Its complex structure is formed by the combining and subordination of partial structures from various arts.

Drawing parallels, superposition and projection of the expressive means belonging to various art forms on the software aspect of organization allows one to organize the expressive means of a multimedia presentation.

In this paper, a comparison is made of the informational/programmatic, and compositional sides of the formation of multimedia presentations. Levels of the composite organization of presentation are determined during the transfer of expressive means of formally similar arts to the levels of logical organization.

The shaping in the logical organization of multimedia presentations is decomposed into two aspects: hypertext system and software interface (Figure 3). An abstract logical organization of data is accompanied by their organization in a definite shape. At the same time there is a correlation between the abstract information and a definite spatial construction, as well as a correlation of abstract programs and a definite temporary construction. Strategy is developed in parallel with the concept. Whereas the content and the functionality are the material from which a work of art is created. The information architecture and the hypertext plots form both a virtual space and the subjects of its examination in time, correspondingly. The navigation and the interface are developed mainly by means of typography and dynamic means of plastic arts. The page layout is visualized mainly by means of graphic design, whereas a set of pages is harmonized in the montage (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Spatial and temporal aspects of compositional organization

The foundation for the design of any message is its thought. Thought is formulated at the strategic level in the informational/programmatic organization. In parallel with the level of strategy, we are positioning the level of concept for the compositional organization of multimedia presentations. Design concept formulated as ‘the central artistic project idea’ is accompanied by the strategies, which are able to empower a technical development of the project (Figure 5).

1. Level of strategy

1. Level of concept

Planning of information and programmatic organization of the message

Imagination of figurative composition of the message

Figure 5. Drawing parallels between the level of strategy and the level of concept

Textual and visual documental materials serve as building blocks for the construction of an artistic space. Software features are the building blocks for the construction of an interactive time frame through the elemental content of the composition. Multimedia presentation is constructed from the variously assorted sources of information. The information comes as text, images, sounds, and software features. If one draws a parallel between the level of scope and the level of the elemental content of the composition, one can see the following: data on the informational/programmatic side are only a speculative list of illustrations and references to the relevant sections, whereas on the composite side these data are transformed into a tangible stack of images that the viewer can sort interactively, for example, through pushing one from the other (Figure 6).

Information architecture is visualized in the virtual space. The interaction scenarios are visualized in the multivariate hypertext storylines. Creating a virtual space and the options for interaction with it can be compared with the development of a story and a plot, say for a film or a novel. A story is a set of information units systematically placed in the space-time continuum, whereas a plot is the rigid sequence in which the user (reader, viewer, spectator) gets these units. Organization of the virtual space is comparable to the organization of the exhibition where the network of the node pages is an accomplished module, each page being a separate collection of ‘artefacts’ associated with the whole system of organization, naming, and navigation.

Unlike the masterpieces of an exhibition existing in a real environment, the information of multimedia presentation is distributed in the virtual space. We consider the system of information blocks associated by harmonic relationships as a virtual three-dimensional composition level of an edition. This level of composition is characterized by the fact that it cannot be seen instantly, but instead it can be presented through the interactive sorting of its parts, and its echoes on the surface of the screen. This level can be seen instantly only with the means of simulation. As an example, a colour-graphical model of the three-dimensional level of the website of Domus Academy (2011), in comparison with its hypertext structure, is shown in Figure 7.

Navigation systems provide orientation in the virtual space. They are most often expressed visually in the colour palette coding and labelling pages or the typography. Movement

through the virtual space is provided by the interface. Interface elements are expressed by the typographical release, e.g., by an explicit graphical isolation of the areas from the content, or by the form changes, which are dictated by an event. The interface shows the navigation through the formatting: links are encoded with the appropriate colour section; some complex

elements (e.g., the drop-down lists) display the structure in a minimized form. Modification of an interface creates different types of intra-movement: moving, panning, dragging, zooming, etc. Visual organization of the navigation and the interface forms a spatio-temporal composition level of the multimedia presentation (Figure 8).

2. Level of scope

2. Level of compositional elements

```
//var imagePath1 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_SCU_Schaffner_PRO-09_1.JPG';
var imagePath1 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_logo_pixel_rca_026.jpg';
var imagePath2 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_SCU_Schaffner_PRO-09_1.JPG';
var imagePath3 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_GSM_Schaffner_PRO-09_1.jpg';
var imagePath4 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_1Rabbitpunch.flv.jpg';
var imagePath5 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_TEX_PRO-09_1.jpg';
var imagePath6 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_CML_of11.jpg';
var imagePath7 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_NCM_Schaffner_PRO-09_1.JPG';
var imagePath8 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_apple-iphone-in-hand-thumb.jpg';
var imagePath9 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_MEN_Schaffner_PRO-09_1.JPG';
var imagePath10 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_MIS_PRO-09_2.jpg';
var imagePath11 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_TongueSucker.jpg';
var imagePath12 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_sustain_logo.jpg';
var imagePath13 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_animation2.jpg';
var imagePath14 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_FSS_alys.tomlinson_02.jpg';
var imagePath15 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_di_silhouettes1.jpg';
var imagePath16 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_EXH_Show#CA_01.jpg';
var imagePath17 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_COM_Schaffner_PRO-09_1.jpg';
var imagePath18 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_CarBombier2.JPG';
var imagePath19 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_tony_pic_5.jpg';
var imagePath20 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_dominic_2.jpg';
var imagePath21 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_Tord-Portrait.jpg';
var imagePath22 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_STORY_Schaffner_PRO-09_Vkua_McMorris.JPG';
var imagePath23 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_GSMC_ALDMNH_Karla.jpg';
var imagePath24 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_ABOUT_Pro-09_Soraya.jpg';
var imagePath25 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_ABOUT_Environment.jpg';
var imagePath26 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_PAN_Schaffner_PRO-09_1.JPG';
var imagePath27 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_Inside Outside Inside_3.jpg';
var imagePath28 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_PRO_Schaffner_PRO-09_1.jpg';
var imagePath29 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_ALDMNH_Dyson_seatruck.jpg';
var imagePath30 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_night_show.jpg';
var imagePath31 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_ABOUT_Tomlinson_PRO-09_8.jpg';
var imagePath32 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_BAT_corner_main_view2.jpg';
var imagePath33 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_Inanoll.flv.jpg';
var imagePath34 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_ro_cassiboya.JPG';
var imagePath35 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_CSM_Schaffner_PRO-09_1.JPG';
var imagePath36 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_DSC4057.jpg';
var imagePath14 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_FSS_alys.tomlinson_02.jpg';
var imagePath15 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_di_silhouettes1.jpg';
var imagePath16 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_EXH_Show#CA_01.jpg';
var imagePath17 = '/UploadedImages/sqg_COM_Schaffner_PRO-09_1.jpg';
```


Figure 6. Drawing parallels between the level of scope and the level of compositional elements

3. Level of structure

3. Level of three-dimensional organization

Figure 7. Drawing parallels between the level of structure and the level of three-dimensional organization

4. Level of navigation and interface

4. Level of spatio-temporal organization

MASTER PROGRAMS

- Accessories Design
- Business Design
- Car Design
- Design
- Fashion Design
- Fashion Management
- Interaction Design
- Interior and Living Design
- Service and Experience Design
- Urban Vision and Architectural Design

Figure 8. Drawing parallels between the level of navigation and interface and the level of spatio-temporal organization

Visualized by means of graphic design, pages are mapped to the time by means of cinematography (through montage). Apart from a presentation, any page is a whole composition. Usually the identification zone acts as a dominant, as opposed to the content zone. Graphically accented interface elements serve as the echoes of it. Grouping the items, as well as the textual and illustrative areas, rhythmically organizes the movement at a glance of the page. The movement is supported by the dynamics of a disclosure of interface elements.

On the surface of the screen it is crucial to identify the information in relation to the virtual organization (three-dimensional

or volume-spatial composition level) of the multimedia presentations, because its holistic interpretation is possible only in the space-time mapping of the parts handled on the plane. In each page, on each plane, the representation of virtual forms of presentation is combined with the forms of interaction with virtuality itself, as well as with the forms of meaningful information. The plane of the screen harmonizes the elements of the organization at all levels, creating a flat composition level (Figure 9).

We have found that the two-dimensionality of the multidimensional expressions of the virtual space on the planar screen

5. Level of layout

5. Level of flat organization

Figure 9. Drawing parallels between the level of layout and the level of flat organization

causes mutual interdependence of the elements and the means of three-dimensional and two-dimensional composition. It thus suggests their connection through the elements and through the spatio-temporal composition that occur when deploying an interactive presentation in spatio-temporal space.

Thus, the projection of artistic means of expression at the informational/programmatic organization of the site allowed us to identify the levels of organization of the composite multimedia presentation: (1) the level of concept, (2) the level of the compositional elements, (3) the three-dimensional compositional level, (4) the spatio-temporal level of composition, and (5) the flat compositional level. The scheme of compositional organization is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Compositional organization

CONCLUSIONS

A multimedia presentation is a form of social communication, which has both an information and a communication function. A message is perceived by the person both rationally and emotionally, necessitating both logical and imaginative formation. Combining the logical and the imaginative structures is implemented in the synthesis of informational/programmatic and compositional organization of multimedia presentations.

Logical organization of the forms of multimedia presentation includes information and software aspects. A scheme of informational/programmatic organization includes (1) the level of strategy, (2) the level of scope, (3) the level of hypertext structure, (4) the level of navigation and interface, and (5) the layout level.

A visual, or shaped, organization of the form of multimedia presentation is carried out both in space and in time. The elements of this form are structured in a virtual environment, forming a three-dimensional composition. Space unfolds on the pages of the edition in the spatio-temporal composition, whereas each page is organized as a planar composition.

A compositional organization of the forms of multimedia presentation comprises (1) the level of concept, (2) the level of compositional elements, (3) the three-dimensional compositional level, (4) the spatio-temporal compositional level, and (5) the flat compositional level. An artistic form of a multimedia presentation is created as a holistic integration of a three-dimensional, spatio-temporal and in-plane composition.

To conclude, we adjusted the Garrett web design model to apply it to the case of multimedia presentation by adding an emotional component on each level. Thus, we supplemented the 'Elements of User Experience' by the 'Elements of Viewer Experience'. Today we are faced with the fact that the user experience has become a central focus for the usability of technology (McCarthy & Wright, 2004). Consequently, users of interactive technologies are now considered as complex, emotional experiencers (Mattelmäki, 2006). Based on our own experience, we analysed the human expectations both from the user and viewer standpoints, and created the ways that help deliver better design solutions.

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SHARING IMAGINATION AND EMOTION THROUGH THE USE OF LIVELY INTERACTIVE PRODUCTS

Kenny K. N. Chow, PhD
School of Design
The Hong Kong Polytechnic University
✉ sdnchow@polyu.edu.hk

ABSTRACT

People using the same product may also share meaning and affect. Grounded in phenomenology in philosophy, cognitive semantics in cognitive science, and the psychology of emotion, this paper argues that lively interactive products, which feature dynamic images with reactivity and contingency, can evoke shared mental images and feelings via familiar sensorimotor experience in two states of interaction, namely continuous feedback (i.e., coupling of user input and system feedback) and extended change (i.e., system change while input pauses). The overall enduring interaction triggers imaginative conceptual blends in users at multiple cognitive levels. Meanwhile, emotions are elicited during different moments. Users thus echo similar imagined thoughts and feelings through the use. This paper introduces interpretive analysis for designers or researchers, showing how the model assists in analyzing inter-subjective user experiences and opens up possibilities for creating more socially resonating products.

KEYWORDS: *Embodied cognition; imagination; emotion; interaction design; sensorimotor experience.*

INTRODUCTION

Through product use people often experience subjectively in terms of the involved sensory perception and bodily action, the memory, meaning, and emotion provoked, and the aesthetics presented. Meanwhile, a good design is able to provide a coherent experience to its users. Users experiencing the same design, especially among those which enable sharing may also recall common memories and share similar thoughts and feelings. This kind of experience belongs to the category of evocation, which is one of the hedonic product attributes delineated by Marc Hassenzahl (2003). Hassenzahl differentiated from pragmatic dimensions of user experience (UX), the three hedonic attributes, namely stimulation (users' personal growth), identification (users' self-expression as compared with others), and evocation (users' memories). Regarding evocation, Hassenzahl's discussion focuses on the relationship between products and single users. In fact, evocation can be extended to include multiple users engaged in shared memories, mental images, and feelings. Hence, evocative experience demonstrates a way toward what Jodi Forlizzi, Katja Battarbee, and Ilpo Koskinen called 'co-experience', which means a group of users co-creating meaning and emotion through the use of a product (Battarbee & Koskinen, 2008; Forlizzi & Battarbee, 2004).

Compared with such pragmatic dimensions of UX as efficiency and usability, which have been well addressed in the tradition of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and have become scientifically 'measurable' by user-evaluation approaches, other attributes like meaning and affect are too abstract and subjective to be accessed. Hendrik N. J. Schifferstein and Paul Hekkert (2008) edited a comprehensive volume of articles revolving around diverse facets of subjective experience of products. They advocated empirical approaches to studying these subjective dimensions via people's self-reporting (Schifferstein & Hekkert, 2008, p.5). Hassenzahl and Noam Tractinsky (2006) also believe that there have been enough conceptual investigations of UX, and more empirical research is required to advance the theories. After their calls, empirical studies of UX have been extended to relatively abstract facets like pleasantness and engagement (Hassenzahl et al., 2010; O'Brien, 2010; Rozendaal & Schifferstein, 2010). Yet, when dealing with the evocation of shared memories, past or inferred experiences, imagery, and affect, it is still controversial to assess these solely empirically. I argue that in the design process user evaluation should come with designer interpretation, because the former is assessment of the current state and therefore might not inform insights for future possibilities. In contrast, the latter, while theoretically grounded, can generate promising ideas for discovering new opportunities.

Designery interpretive analysis can be applied in analyzing existing design artifacts (which connects the past to the current) as well as developing new ones (which connects the current to the future). This paper thus offers an interpretive approach grounded in embodied cognition ideas of the topic of inter-subjective experiences of interactive products. It first introduces the idea of what I call 'lively interactive products', followed by underlying concepts including those from phenomenology, cognitive semantics, and the psychology of emotion, which relates the characteristics of lively interactive products, including reactivity and contingency, to people's imagination and affect via sensory perception and motor action. Lastly, it illustrates the notion by an array of existing and developing design artifacts.

LIVELY INTERACTIVE PRODUCTS

Everyday products by convention afford (offer the possibility of) motor action to people. By affordances, we follow J. J. Gibson's ecological approach (Gibson, 1977; Kannengiesser & Gero, 2011). For example, a bed affords the action of lying down. A task chair affords the act of sitting upright and concentrating on the desktop work. On the other hand, some cases can involve multiple users. A couch affords to several people the act of sitting at a reclined position and enjoying the television. The television is intended to simultaneously engage several people's attention towards its media content. A user can press buttons, either on the set or on the remote control, to select a favorite channel and enjoy with his or her companions. Sometimes, one may ask another to adjust the speaker volume. The group then listens to the television's instant and incremental feedback on the audio level, until someone says the level is good and the enjoyment continues. It may happen that the audio level later becomes apparently too loud, probably due to a commercial break, a particular voice over, or the antenna reception, and one may need to adjust the volume again. In this scenario, the television demonstrates a certain degree of liveliness. It is reactive to user input, but also contingent upon other factors during the period of delivery.

By liveliness, I mean an interactive product that affords continuous motor action and perception of enduring change to the user in two states. On occasions, the user may perform continuous motor input and simultaneously perceive incremental change presented by the product without practical time lag, that is, a continuous sensorimotor feedback loop between the user and the product (Figure 1). On the other, the user may just perceive the change continuing indefinitely without giving any input. The user is probably engaged in subtle motor action (e.g., moving the eyeballs, or coming closer to peep, etc.; i.e., perception involves a certain degree of motor action), but the action is not an input to the feedback loop. The loop is temporarily suspended (Figure 2), and the change becomes indefinite and contingent upon other factors. In short, a lively interactive product features both reactivity and contingency. The overall change demonstrates a kind of 'enduring interaction' (Chow, 2012; Chow & Harrell, 2011).

Figure 1 Continuous feedback loops between users and lively interactive objects feature reactivity.

Figure 2 Indefinite change with temporary suspension of motor input implies contingency.

The phenomenon of enduring interaction exists in the use of many everyday things. Consider baking coffee with companions using a French press. You pour water into the beaker continuously until the rising water level reaches the desired marker or someone suggests a stop. You and your friends then observe the changing color inside the container or the aroma arising from it, until someone expresses that it is time to press the filter and enjoy. You and your companions try to control and fine-tune the current states toward the desired results (e.g., appropriate amount, temperature, and concentration). One is continuously engaged in motor action (e.g., pouring water, and then the coffee) and sensory perception (e.g., observing the water level, and the coffee color). Other examples include the tandem-riding experience. Both front and rear riders actively engage in cycling the pedals but only the former can steer with the handlebar. Meanwhile, both of them are sensing the resultant speed and changing direction. Sometimes, one may want to pause cycling and let the bicycle run freely. During these relatively inactive moments, the riders still keep sensing the change in speed (contingent upon the slope of the road) and may resume action soon. These common examples show that enduring interaction takes place in the use of many everyday things. At reactive moments, we act to input and perceive the output continuously and simultaneously. During contingent moments, we just perceive how a situation continues to change indefinitely. If the use of an interactive product is reminiscent of an enduring interaction in people's past events or memories, the product can invoke shared imagination and affect among them. The following section provides the theoretical underpinning of this argument.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

For interactive products to evoke imagination and affect, lively attributes including reactivity and contingency are crucial. At reactive moments, the product use entails cognitive coupling of sensory perception and motor action, triggering users' impulsive desires, automatic appraisals, and immediate conceptual blends. During contingent moments, the product continues to show changes, suggesting to users imagined narratives via metaphorical blends and eliciting their emotions via extended appraisals of an apparent reality.

Cognitive coupling of sensory perception and motor action

The coupling of sensory perception and motor action has been central to the seminal study of developmental psychology initiated by the philosopher and psychologist Jean Piaget. To Piaget, infancy or what he called 'sensorimotor stage' is foundational to the development of one's cognition via simple acts like sucking and looking (Thelen, 1995, p.73). The computer scientist Ben Shneiderman, drawing upon Piaget, coined the term 'direct manipulation' and influenced the design of graphical user interfaces (GUI). The idea specifies physical action (e.g., the drag-and-drop mouse action) and visible feedback (e.g., change of appearance when an item is selected), bringing human-computer activity back to the level of early child development, which is easy to use and learn (Shneiderman, 2003 [1983]). Lately, S. A. G. Wensveen, J. P. Djajadiningrat, and C. J. Overbeeke have proposed a vigorous framework of coupling of action and feedback (Wensveen, Djajadiningrat, & Overbeeke, 2004). It introduces six aspects of coupling, including time, location, direction, dynamics (continuous or discrete motion), modality (sight, sound, or touch), and expression (related to users' states). Natural coupling should have no delay in time between action and feedback, both of which should take place at the same location and along the same direction. Continuity or discreteness of motion has to be consistent too. Among various aspects, I argue continuity in time and modality is more essential than location and direction for natural coupling in the use of lively interactive products.

In cognitive science, Esther Thelen has shown that infants start to develop various simple motor skills, such as reaching out or grasping, through continuous processes of 'integrated acts' of moving body parts and perceiving changes in environments. These changes vary continuously and infinitesimally, and a baby incrementally learns the force required to move muscles to an appropriate extent in a particular context (Thelen, 1995, p.90). Consider using a computer mouse to drag a file icon onto a folder icon in a GUI environment. A user keeps sliding the mouse while tracking the file icon moving on the display until it reaches the folder. This sensorimotor phenomenon is comparable to our physical experience of moving a piece of paper from the desk into a tray. When continuously moving our body parts, we need to simultaneously 'see' something being 'moved' from one location to another. Though the GUI

environment demands some kind of learning curve at first, a user can easily master the skill without noticing details of his or her action after some repetitions. This shows that with continuous feedback loops our bodies have the power to 'cognitively naturalize' a coupling even though the action and feedback mismatch in location and direction. This phenomenon is further explained in the next section.

Conceptual blends, material anchors, and material-based imagination

Lively interactive products entail coupling of action and perception, which readily invokes imagination in users. At reactive moments, the sensorimotor feedback loop, augmented with the dynamic change presented by the product, is usually reminiscent of one's past experiences. For example, PEGA D&E's Pumplight is a balloon-shaped table lamp (<http://www.pegadesign.com/en/portfolio-pumplight.html>), which has a pump (like those usually found in blood pressure meters) in place of the common switch. A user can inflate the balloon using the pump. When the balloon gets bigger, the light becomes brighter. The analogy in sensorimotor phenomenon readily and immediately provokes an imagined concept of 'pumping' energy into the lamp, that is, a blended image in users. During contingent moments, extended change without user input brings a set of related knowledge (in cognitive science's terms, 'frames') to the user's mind, yielding more elaborate imagination. For instance, TH Design's Tio is an intriguing eco-friendly light switch that shows changing color after the light is on (<http://timholley.de/2010/08/10/tio/>). It gradually turns from green to orange and then red in an eight-hour period, aiming to remind users of energy conservation. The changing color, together with emoticon-like facial expressions, invokes the 'tolerance' frame in users, suggesting an imaginative narrative of someone feeling annoyed with the light being on for too long. This is what Kenny K. N. Chow and D. Fox Harrell call 'material-based imagination' (Chow & Harrell, 2009; Chow & Harrell, 2012), grounded in theories of conceptual blends and material anchors, both from cognitive science.

Imagination (i.e., mental imagery) based on material images can take place at the automatic, perceptual level. Arguments suggesting a close relationship between mental images and perception include those of Ludwig Wittgenstein as described by Mitchell (1986), Arnheim (1969), Stafford (2007), and Johnson (2008). Once viewers perceive a material artifact as associated with some meaning (e.g., a clock face), the perceived image becomes a mental image (i.e., one can 'see' the displayed time even with eyes closed). Edwin Hutchins's concept of material anchors (2005) reciprocally theorizes the distribution of meaning (e.g., the time) onto physical structures (e.g., the clock face with the hands). Material anchors are structures or patterns that 'hold' crucial information in place for mental manipulation. In the case of an analog stopwatch, the position of the stopwatch's minute hand and the target time marking on its face form a circular sector that, when considered relative to a complete circle, informs the

user of the time left. Such a material image in the physical world can carry information for direct input to cognitive processes like conceptual blending.

Building upon the earlier concepts of mental spaces (Fauconnier, 1985) and conceptual metaphors (Lakoff & Johnson, 2003), Gilles Fauconnier and Mark Turner (2002) argue that conceptual blending is a basic mental operation that generates new meanings by integrating concepts, and forming emergent networks. Blending is pervasive in common sense meaning making, as well as in other creative feats like rhetoric, gameplay, and even in interface design (Fauconnier, 2001, p.279). Some blends can be so commonly exercised in everyday life that they become automatic and unnoticed. Fauconnier has cited the computer interface phenomenon as an example of this kind of immediate blend (pp. 264-65). For instance, a user dragging a window on a computer desktop slides the mouse on a real horizontal desk. Meanwhile, the user's eyes track the vertically-oriented movement of the graphics on the screen. There are a set of mappings between the physical space and the screen space, including from the mouse to the window, from the mouse click to the act of 'picking-up' the window, from forward to up, from backward to down, and so on. Most users, however, are unaware of the blend. They just feel that they are directly manipulating the window. This action-perception coupling seems to violate at least two aspects of Wensveen, et al. (2004)'s natural coupling, namely unified location and direction, but it becomes second nature to many computer users of today. This is indeed the power of conceptual blends enabled by interactive systems.

Chow and Harrell extend the above ideas to argue that interactive dynamic images (offered by lively interactive systems) can act as elastic material anchors for imaginative conceptual blends (Chow & Harrell, 2013). These images hold distilled dynamic information (like Pumplight's varied balloon size), and mobilize continuous sensorimotor feedback loops, provoking at reactive moments immediate imaginative blends that bridge the gaps in location or direction. During contingent moments, the images continue to change without user input (like Tio's changing color and emoticon). The perception of change usually gives users a concept of time. As the philosopher and psychologist William James puts it, 'awareness of change is [...] the condition on which our perception of time's flow depends' (1890, p.620). Psychologist J. J. Gibson also said that 'external stimuli [...] provide a flow of change, and it is this we perceive rather than a flow of time as such' (Gibson, 1975, p.299). Perception of change brings a set of concepts about time, including order, duration, beginning, and end. These temporal elements, together with the information held by the images, constitute the essence of an experience, or a narrative. Dewey has distinguished 'an experience' from 'experience'. The former is singular, 'having its own beginning and end' (Dewey, 1980, pp.35-36). Hence, an experience is comparable to a narrative. A sensorimotor experience of change readily provokes higher levels of imaginative blends in the form of narrative, which Chow and Harrell call metaphorical blends. Illustrative examples will follow in later sections.

Desire, appraisal, and the laws of emotion

Lively interactive products allow users to perform continuous motor action as input and to perceive enduring change. To really engage users in the sensorimotor phenomena, two components pertaining to affect are required. They are desire and appraisal.

Motor action and desire

From the phenomenologist point of view, continuous motor action or bodily motion embodies one's intention, desire, and so emotion. The continuity in time or motion is the key. Maurice Merleau-Ponty believes that through repeated practice our body can 'absorb' motor knowledge from the environment we inhabit and turn it into situated motor habits (Merleau-Ponty, 1962, pp.146-147). He called this the 'intentional arc', which is the 'power of laying out a past in order to move toward a future' (Merleau-Ponty, 1962, pp.135-136). The intentional arc exists in both space and time and works beneath the level of reflective thought. In other words, bodily motion embodies one's pre-reflective intention toward a desirable future state. Some thinkers have further argued that pre-reflective bodily motion is closely tied to one's emotion. To Roberta De Monticelli, emotions are 'vectors of (impulsive) action and of immediate action' (Monticelli, 2006, p.74). Michelle Maiese points out that emotion is based on one's impulsive, spontaneous, and pre-reflective intention to move the body self-expressively (Maiese, 2011, pp.62-63). This impulse is our first-order desire of 'wanting or not wanting things to be a certain way'. For instance, one feeling irritated about a radio commercial immediately turns the volume control knob anti-clockwise before any reflective thought. This is because the continuous nature of the knob fits the intentional arc. After repeated engagement one acquires the habit of turning the knob clockwise (or anti-clockwise) toward something desirable (or away from the undesirable). When one feels a need or want, the body spontaneously performs the corresponding movements that constitute embodiment of the desire. Hence, a lively interactive system affording continuous motor input with instant feedback tends to encourage users to act out their desires, and repeated engagement turns their actions into motor habits to express affective preferences. It follows that a radio receiver equipped with the variable volume control knob is more inviting to users' emotional impulses than one with only the toggle switch. The discrete nature of the latter hinders the habituation of affective motor action.

Perceivable change and appraisal

Lively interactive products feature perceivable enduring change. During both reactive and contingent moments, users assess the current state against the desired through perception. In addition to desire, assessment, or appraisal constitutes the core of our affect. To represent the raw feelings that exist within us, James A. Russell (2003) proposes what he calls 'core affect', a matrix of two dimensions, namely pleasantness and arousal. Pleasantness is 'an assessment of one's current condition', whereas arousal is 'one's sense of mobilization and

energy'. Russell believes that all moods and emotions can be reduced to a blend of the two dimensions, and this 'core affect is a continuous assessment of one's current state'. More importantly, this kind of assessment is often done via perception. As De Monticelli writes, 'feeling is essentially the perception of values' of things, and it can be positive or negative (Monticelli, 2006, pp.65-66). The alignment of Russell's and De Monticelli's views suggests that continuous assessment via perception constitutes our raw feelings. Another technical term for assessment is 'appraisal'. Paul Ekman has described appraisal of a current event as one of the characteristics of emotion (Ekman, 1992; 1994). He points out that the appraisal mechanism can operate automatically at the primary level or sometimes take place more reflectively at higher cognitive levels. The two mechanisms, namely *automatic* and *extended*, suggest appraisals of the enduring changes of interactive products during reactive and contingent moments respectively. Hence, at reactive moments impulsive desire and automatic appraisal join to result in affect. At contingent moments, extended appraisal may take place..

The laws of emotion

Lastly, Nico H. Frijda's two particular laws of emotion (1988), among others, also give support to the evocative power of lively interactive products. First, the law of change specifies that emotions are elicited by 'actual or expected changes in favorable or unfavorable conditions'. It is the change with respect to the current state that affects how a person feels. The enduring change presented by lively interactive products readily provokes users' emotional responses. Second, the law of apparent reality states that emotions are elicited by events that seem to be real. Images, pictures, photographs, sounds or voices, are taken to be more vivid and serious than words. As argued above, lively interactive products featuring dynamic images (or other sensory data) with enduring changes trigger imaginative blends, yielding immersive mental imagery. It follows from the above two laws that users will appraise the changes in the imagined situation as vividly real, and have emotions evoked.

INTERPRETIVE ANALYSES OF SHARING LIVELY INTERACTIVE PRODUCTS

Lively interactive products feature dynamic images with both reactivity and contingency, which are reminiscent of users' past or inferred experiences. This kind of embodied analogy provokes imagination in terms of conceptual blends at multiple levels and elicits emotion at different moments of interaction. This brings about the inter-subjective experience resonating among a group of shared users.

In summary, the analysis of inter-subjective experience includes the mappings from users' sensorimotor experiences to their cognitive and affective responses during the two states of interaction. The following two tables (Table 1 and 2) put together related aspects for considering the mappings:

SENSORIMOTOR EXPERIENCES	FOR IMAGINATIVE AND AFFECTIVE RESPONSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Users' motor input - Product's sensory feedback (including images, sounds, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sensorimotor feedback loop anchoring an embodied concept - <i>Immediate</i> blend with past or inferred experiences outputting a new concept - <i>Impulsive</i> desire and <i>automatic</i> appraisal leading to emotional response

Table 1. Mapping experiences during reactive moments

SENSORIMOTOR EXPERIENCES	FOR IMAGINATIVE AND AFFECTIVE RESPONSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Product's overall enduring change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enduring change invoking a semantic frame - <i>Metaphorical</i> blend outputting imagined narrative like apparent reality - <i>Apparent reality</i> and <i>extended</i> appraisal leading to emotional response

Table 2: Mapping experiences during contingent moments

During reactive moments, the sensorimotor feedback loop has to be compared to certain common sensorimotor phenomenon in the user's everyday life, anchoring an embodied concept for *immediate blending*. The output of the blend will be an imagination. Meanwhile, the user's motor action has to be associated with an *impulsive desire*, and the object's instant feedback lets the user perform *automatic appraisal*, resulting in either a positive or negative affect (e.g., satisfaction, discontent, etc.). The affect also helps mobilize the sensorimotor feedback loop.

During contingent moments, the overall enduring change has to be in focus. It suggests a semantic frame with temporal and contingent elements, informing components to be mapped with those elaborated from the immediate blend and additionally the changes the user later perceives. These form the *metaphorical blend*, proposing an imaginative narrative or scenario. This material-based imagination has vivid images, and the user is engrossed in this *apparent reality* assessing the changing state. This *extended appraisal* results in further emotional responses.

To illustrate how the above model assists in understanding scenarios for people to share mental imagery and affect, analyses of sharing lively interactive products follow. They include a physical board game, a digital and tangible photo album, and a smart device for sharing umbrellas. The first one is an existing product, which represents the emergence of liveliness in today's design trends. The other two are artifacts designed and developed by students in School of Design, The Hong Kong

Polytechnic University, demonstrating how the proposed model can be applied in design processes.

The board game MELTDOWN

GEOLino MELTDOWN (<http://meltdown-game.com>) is a board game for a group of two to four players, aged five or above. Players prepare ice cubes with the given tray and then flip them onto the given spongy sheet to form the game board. The aim of the game is to move the polar bear-like tokens according to rolled dice before the ice melts beneath them (see Figure 3).

Figure 3 GEOLino MELTDOWN requires players to save the polar bears before the ice melts.

When players take turns to roll the dice, move the bears, and see them advancing, the game presents a dynamic image of pacing bears on the melting ice. To a player, this sensorimotor experience is reminiscent of playing common roll-and-move games like *The Game of Life*. The immediate blend is a family of bears running towards the larger center ice cube according to the dice. The blend allows the players to easily understand the gameplay, such as turn taking, moving steps, possible paths, and destination (that is also one of the common functions of conceptual blends in our everyday lives). Knowing the game goal, each player has an impulse to move a bear every time the dice are rolled. Seeing the dice and moving the bear,

one automatically appraises the result, which may be exciting or disappointing. The impulsive desire and automatic appraisal keep players in the sensorimotor feedback loop. Since the game is a cooperative game, all players should yield the similar blend, sharing the ups and downs during play.

The most intriguing mechanic of the game is that the ice cubes are melting enduringly. Even though it is not the turn for a particular player to move, one can still see the cubes going away. The meltdown time is contingent upon the room temperature, the ice condition, and other factors. This enduring change, together with the move-and-stop bears and the blue sponge, easily invokes the frame of global warming effects on the Arctic with temporal elements like time limit and order of meltdown. The metaphorical blend generates an imaginative narrative that resembles those documentary videos we saw on television shows in which a polar bear is hopelessly trapped in an isolated, small piece of floating ice and cannot get to the main iceberg nearby. It echoes the game's tagline, 'save the polar bears before the ice melts'. The imagined story, augmented with all the dynamic images, is so apparently real that it vividly immerses the whole group of players. They play and share the resulting feelings such as blessing, disappointment, or even regret. One might also wonder if the game outcomes shed any light on the real cases in the Arctic. Indeed, the game wishes to bring awareness of the topic to its target players.

Photo Turntable: a digital and tangible photo album

The second example is a new design by a graduate student (Yang Pu) from School of Design, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University. It is a tangible interactive system, providing new user experience in storing, organizing, and sharing digital photos. The concept combines traditional photo albums and vinyl music records into a special disc. To browse the photos, users just put the disc on the given turntable and spin it. The photos associated with the disc can be viewed either via a computer screen, or projected on the wall via the built-in projector, which facilitates sharing among a group in gathering (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. The Photo Turntable system includes physical product and software, allowing users to organize, view, and share photo collections in a tangible, nostalgic way.

When a user spins the disc, one can see the photos flipping consecutively. This continuous sensorimotor phenomenon is reminiscent of the past or inferred (after seeing others doing it) experience of turntable scratching or the use of the jog dial on professional videotape recorders, spinning clockwise to play forward and anticlockwise to rewind. The immediate blend results in a concept of photo record, which allows sequential access to photos with a rotary control. One's finger motion, including speed and direction, conveys the impulsive desire of viewing photos in succeeding or preceding order. Seeing the photos in sequence, one automatically appraises whether the previous or next photo is more interesting than the current one, and spins the disc anticlockwise or clockwise. The impulsive desire and automatic appraisal sustains the sensorimotor feedback loop.

Instead of looking for a target, the user may want to enjoy the album generally. If so, one can just press a button to let the turntable rev the disc, and then the photos will be shown in a slideshow. The show is contingent upon the particular disc content and the selected play mode. One can view the show with others in a gathering and share the pleasurable moments. The spinning disc with printed cover, the turntable, and the slideshow join to form an immersive relaxing atmosphere, evocative of listening to the gramophone with company in the old times. This invokes the corresponding frame. The metaphorical blend can be an imaginative narrative of friends coming to appreciate one's favorite albums. Based on friends' responses, one may appraise whether the current collection (of photos) is interesting to the 'audience'. All in all, viewing photos together and taking a glimpse of friends' exciting responses embody the happiness.

Umbrella Here: a smart device for sharing umbrellas

Umbrella Here (<http://www.umbrellahere.com/>) is another developing interactive smart device designed by a group of

students (Tommy Lau, Martin Tsang, Karen Wan, & Patience Lee) from School of Design, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University. The small device can sit on the desk indoors and connect to the owner's smartphone, receiving weather reports from the Internet and glowing differently with corresponding colors to remind him or her of bringing an umbrella. If attached, it makes the umbrella smart. It not only sends you notification of being left behind out of home, but more intriguingly, it glows at the top of the umbrella if it is put up in the rain. The light signals that the user is willing to share the umbrella with others. The device aims to mobilize mutual sharing between people (Figure 5).

When the user puts up the umbrella and walks in the rain, he or she can turn on the attached device light (through the smartphone) to invite people. If someone comes in and asks to share the umbrella, the user can turn the light off (or keep it on if the umbrella still has room!). The operation makes the user feel like they are doing a taxi driver's job. The analogy builds upon the sensorimotor experience of turning the light on and seeing someone search for a ride. Yet, this 'umbrella ride' is for sharing rather than hiring. The immediate blend outputs a new concept of inviting people to a free umbrella ride. To someone running across the street soaking-wet, the device light seems to be a lighthouse bringing hope in the heavy rain. To the 'umbrella driver', a 'passenger's' hopeful and thankful face is also very delightful.

When the user stays indoors, he or she may not actively engage with the device. It sits on the desk or table and enduringly glows in changing colors with the updated weather condition. The enduring and contingent (it's weather!) change does not just practically remind the user to bring an umbrella, but also emotionally signals that it is time to help others by giving a free ride again! It invokes the emergency service frame, which consists of elements like emergency call, person in need, urgency, safety, and so on. The device's glowing light is analogical to an

Figure 5 Umbrella Here can be attached to an umbrella to invite passers-by who get wet, or it can sit on a desk to show different colors based on an updated weather report.

emergency call, provoking images of someone getting wet in the street, waiting restlessly under a shelter, or even sliding on a slope. The metaphorical blend of the glowing light with the emergency call results in an imaginative narrative with the message: 'bring the umbrella and help others!'

Based on the proposed model summarized in Table 1 and 2, suggestions can be given on how to make the sensorimotor experience of putting up the inviting signal more embodied, and how to make the emergency signal more enduring for extended appraisal. The former includes more thoughts on gestural input, for example, shaking the smartphone up to raise the signal and shaking down to turn it off. The latter can be mapping different shades of color to the updated rain precipitation measurement. The user can then perceive the color darkening over a period of time and know the situation outdoors is getting worse. One would become increasingly worried about people outside.

CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

Lively interactive products feature dynamic images and enduring interaction, enabling imaginative conceptual blends at multiple levels, and eliciting affective responses at different moments. Hence, a group of users may share imagination and emotion through the product use. The interpretive analyses shown in this paper resonate with Forlizzi and Battarbee's suggestion for designers and researchers, 'mapping smaller experiences inside bigger ones' in order to 'understand relationships between small and large' (Forlizzi & Battarbee, 2004). Mapping sensorimotor experiences is important to understanding thought and feeling elicited in sharing interactive products. Meanwhile, it is well noted that the above interpretive analyses should be cross-referenced by empirical evaluation studies. Possible methods include retrospective self-reporting and prospective probing. Future empirical research is required to strengthen the proposition.

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DESIGNING FOR SELF-ACTUALIZATION IN CHILDHOOD

Tatiana Mejía Piedrahita
Delft University of Technology. Faculty of Industrial Design Engineering
✉ tatymejia82@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

According to Maslow's hierarchy of needs, self-actualization, which is the motive to realize one's full potential, represents a final level of psychological development. Maslow proposed that, in order to have the ability to self-actualize, an individual needs to fulfil all lower-order (deficiency) needs, such as safety and esteem. Moreover, fulfilling these lower-order needs is a requirement but not a guarantee to reach self-actualization because this requires particular skills and mind-sets. Taking into account that only a small number of adults can reach this level, it seems relevant to explore if and how the ability to self-actualize can be developed and supported from childhood. This paper reports an initial exploration of the question of whether it is possible to design for stimulating self-actualization in children in the context of education. Some key literature is discussed and design directions are proposed.

KEYWORDS: *Self-actualization, Children, Design, Learning environments, Education*

INTRODUCTION

'Human life will never be understood unless its highest aspirations are taken into account.'

(Maslow, 1970, p. XX)

Abraham H. Maslow dedicated his life to the study of people that he considered to be psychologically healthy, an ambition he expressed in his influential book *Towards a Psychology of Being*: 'Indeed, self-actualizing people, those who have come to a high level of maturation, health and self-fulfilment, have so much to teach us that sometimes they seem almost like a different breed of human beings' (Maslow, 1970, p.71). He proposed that human behaviour could be motivated either by deficiency-needs (such as physiological needs and safety needs) or growth-needs (or 'growth values'), and that humans self-actualize when motivated by growth values. Growth values include truth, creativity, beauty, goodness, wholeness, aliveness, uniqueness, justice, simplicity, and self-sufficiency, and are not imposed by religion or culture, but rather naturally developed by healthy human beings:

In addition to Darwinian survival value, we may now also postulate "growth values." Not only is it good to survive, but it is also good (preferred, choices, good for the organism) for the person to grow toward full humanness, towards actualization of potentials, toward greater happiness, serenity, peak experiences, toward transcendence, toward richer and more accurate cognition of reality, and so on. No longer need we rest on sheer viability

and survival as our only ultimate proof that poverty or war or domination or cruelty are bad, rather than good. We can consider them bad because they also degrade the quality of life, of personality, of consciousness, of wisdom (Maslow, 1970, p.61).

The ability to self-actualize is not apparent. Maslow stressed that many people choose the worse rather than the better because growth is often a painful process and may for this reason be shunned; we are profoundly ambivalent about our own best possibilities, both fearing and loving them. He also proposed that one is not born self-actualized: being a human being — in the sense of being born to the human species — must be defined also in terms of becoming a human being: 'In this sense a baby is only potentially a human being, and must grow into humanness in the society and the culture, the family' (Maslow, 1970, p.XXIV). An important challenge, Maslow mentioned, is that growth needs require better outside conditions to make them possible than deficiency needs. As an example, he mentions that *good* environmental conditions are necessary to keep people from killing each other, even *better* conditions to allow people to love each other, and *excellent* conditions are required to make self-actualizing possible.

In this paper, we explore some initial ideas of how design can deliberately contribute to conditions for the self-actualization of children. What kind of 'excellent' conditions can be created and how? This exploration connects to the Positive Design Movement, which explores how design can contribute to human flourishing, as introduced by Desmet and Pohlmeier (2014, p.1): 'Now that human happiness is widely

acknowledged to have an important role in human development, it should be given serious attention in the design discipline as well. It deserves to be examined through scientific investigations and some design research. With design being perhaps one of the most intimate means for reaching people, it is time to explore the possibilities it offers for supporting the inherent human aspiration of living a good life'. Pohlmeier (2012) used positive psychology as a resource to positive design, proposing that design can contribute to user well-being in various fashions (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Design for happiness (Pohlmeier, 2012)

Taking into account that children have yet to develop the ability to self-actualize, their environment, including the social, cultural, and material environment, plays a pivotal role in the establishment of virtues and the development of cognitive, social and emotional skills. In this paper, we first discuss the concept of self-actualization, including the required external conditions. Next, some literature is reviewed that discusses the concept of self-actualization in relation to the development (and education) of children. On the basis of this review, we propose some opportunities to design for self-actualization, including design that supports learning and creativity development.

SELF-ACTUALIZATION

At the basis of Maslow's theory is the proposition that humans are dominated and their behaviour is organized by unsatisfied needs. If a hunter is satisfied, it becomes unimportant in the current dynamics of the individual. The most basic consequence of satiation of any need is that this need is submerged and a new and higher need emerges. The consequence of this is that the human being is a wanting animal and rarely reaches a state of complete satisfaction, except for a short time. As one desire is satisfied, another pops up to take its place. When this is satisfied, still another comes to the foreground, and so on. It is a characteristic of human beings throughout their whole lives that they practically always desire something. The higher the need, the less imperative there is for sheer survival, the longer the need can be postponed, and the easier it is for the need to disappear permanently.

Although influential, Maslow's hierarchy of needs has also been subject to criticism. One important critique is that the proposition that one need has to be satisfied to facilitate the satisfaction of the next one is not supported by empirical evidence. Nonetheless, Maslow's work is considered an important foundation for positive psychology because he was one of the first to study healthy people that have demonstrated the ability to flourish (Seligman et al., 2005).

Self-actualization can be considered to be the need to realize one's potential. It refers to the pursuit of becoming what the individual really is and is capable of being, as Maslow said 'What a man can be, he must be'. What is interesting to mention is that one of the most important and universal characteristics that Maslow found in the subjects he studied and considered as self-actualized, is their creativity. It has been shown that creativity also correlates to other important qualities for being self-actualized, for example spontaneity, non-prejudice thinking, and to enjoy the simplest things, among others (Goble, 1970).

Apart from self-actualization, some authors proposed that there is a significant relationship between creativity and subjective well-being, and this connection results in self-acceptance, personal growth, and a sense of having purpose in life (Taman-aeifar & Motaghedifard, 2014). These authors have found that creative thinking is enhanced by a happy and positive mood, contributing to joy and indirectly to reaching self-actualization through the stimulation of some important values.

CHILDREN AND SELF-ACTUALIZATION

Self-actualized people accept themselves and their life circumstances as they are, feel a harmony in their lives and a fulfillment with all they have; are creative individuals, spontaneous, with a big concern about social issues, and can enjoy and appreciate the simplest things of life (Maslow, 1943). Intuitively, some of these characteristics seem to be present in children. Maslow (as reported in Goble, 1970) actually mentioned that he believed that creativity is one of the important characteristics that people tend to lose when growing up. If that is the case, it is interesting to ask: what are the circumstances in the growing process that causes people to lose their creativity? Or, from a designer's point of view, which design strategies can be used to support and maintain creativity in childhood?

Goble (1970) proposed that the creativity of self-actualized people is similar to children's creativity before they learned to fear the ridicule of others, while they are still able to see things freshly and without prejudice. To be creative it is necessary to be spontaneous, that means being able to express what one is feeling or thinking without any mask. Another important characteristic that is found in self-actualized people and children is the way they can see other people and the world, without any preconceptions, seeing them with uncritical and innocent eyes (Goble, 1970).

Burleson (2005) had found that the good development of children depends on the opportunities available for them to be

exposed to the appropriate stimulation in order to acquire all the abilities necessary for positive physical and mental health, and to become an independent and happy adult. The establishment of virtues, habits and skills in childhood are essential for the brain to create patterns of behaviour that hardly change during an entire lifetime, and that define what is going to happen with the child once he or she becomes an adult (Burlleson, 2005).

UNESCO recognize four pillars of education: (UNESCO)

Figure 2. Pillars of education. Own representation.

According to the report: ‘Learning: the treasure within’, in the section “Learning to be’ they stated: ‘the aim of development is the complete fulfilment of man, in all the richness of his personality, the complexity of his forms of expression and his various commitments — as individual, member of a family and of a community, citizen and producer, inventor of techniques and creative dreamer’ (International Commission on Education for the Twenty-first Century, Delors & Unesco, 1996)

In this way, education is not solely about acquiring knowledge, but is also about learning how to discover and getting to know one’s self, others, society and, in general, the world. Ensuring that children will have the sufficient resources and opportunities to understand the world, it is expected that they will be able to fit in and become successful people.

Several authors have stated that through learning and creativity, it is possible to encourage children to become self-actualized people (Burlleson, 2005). They stated that creativity, learning and self-actualization constitute a synergistic cycle, where each stage contributes to achieve the others. Table 1 describes the achievements of some of these authors.

Torrance, 1965	Cultivating early experience and belief in personal creativity is a means for a life-long self-actualization, and to have adults with no sense of uselessness about what they do.
Goble, 1970	Children should be enabled to become more and more what they are, understand what they desire to become, and achieve everything they are capable of becoming.
Soloway	Ownership discovery and experimentation, facilitates self-actualization.
Faure, 1972	The task of education is to preserve individual originality, creativity and ingenuity while preparing the individual for a place in real life.

Table 1. Self-actualization in children (Burlleson, 2005)

According to these authors, education and learning environments could support and stimulate the establishment of important foundations in children to become self-actualized adults, through a learning process focused on letting children discover, experiment, and fail, and in so doing cultivate creativity.

DESIGN OPPORTUNITIES

Design is a field of study that aims to develop products and/or services based on most of the case studies of the needs of market consumers. However, it could also be used to create environments and/or experiences able to support and stimulate behaviours and the establishment of virtues and skills. As the learning process in children occurs in their family and educational context, it is important to design these environments in a way that supports happiness, and stimulates creativity and imagination, in order to let children discover who they are, who they want to become, and what their goals, dreams, and expectations are. Also, by applying some design theories to create products that support the values of children and stimulate the acquisition of skills, the production of self-actualized adults is encouraged. Below are exposed some design approaches that were consulted to explore those possibilities within this field.

Persuasive Design

Is defined as all the strategies implemented to try to change, increase, or establish a new behaviour or attitude of people (Fogg, 2003), through the experience and/or use of products, services and environments. Fogg proposed a behavioural model. He states that in order to persuade people it is first of all necessary that they have the motivation, the ability, and the right triggers to show the desired behaviour (Fogg, 2003).

Persuasive design could be used to design learning environments that persuade children to be creative, to explore their world, to know themselves and others, and to support the development of physical, cognitive, emotional, and social skills. It is also important that the design of objects inside those environments encourage children to be curious, to create, and to share with other children. For example, installing rooms inside kindergartens used to create different things using paints, clay, wooden blocks with different shapes, and tools, among

other elements. A place where children could represent themselves, people around them, and the world as they understand it, or just to build whatever they want and imagine.

The design of an education environment that could fit the description of an environment that persuades children to acquire some skills important to promoting self-actualization from childhood, are the kindergartens of 'Buen Comienzo' (the translation in English is 'good beginning') (Municipio de Medellín, s.f.). This is a program in the Municipality of Medellín, Colombia, which gives children from poor neighbourhoods integral attention from pregnancy.

When children are two years old, they work alongside the kindergartens, designed by the Municipality, to achieve the goal of the program: to give children a good education, and in an environment that promotes the well-being and offers the children the same opportunities as those that attend private institutions. The kindergartens have different types of rooms for: sensory stimulation, a theatre, music, playing and learning. With these rooms they promote the creativity, autonomy, freedom, possibilities of expression, and happiness, among other experiences, that are needed to motivate children towards become self-actualized adults.

Figures 3, 4, and 5 present some of the rooms mentioned above (Municipio de Medellín, s.f.). The images show that the rooms have a very simple design and are equipped with different objects and elements to give children the opportunity to imagine and use those elements to create music, a magic world, to interact with other children, to be sociable individuals, and many other activities encouraging their creativity.

Positive design

Another interesting approach of design that could be supportive to make children more self-actualized, is the positive design. It is focused on looking for products that give people a great experience and makes them feel happy (Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013). A happy person is also someone that tends to be more creative, sociable, and energetic, among other characteristics and values that are needed to be a self-actualized person.

Positive design is looking for a way to use the knowledge from positive psychology, which studies the reasons, conditions, and characteristics needed for people to flourish, be happy, and possess good well-being (TU Delft, s.f.). In positive design there are more focused design approaches in a specific area, for example design for happiness, design for subjective well-being, design for emotions and design for virtues. Those could be applied to design products and/or environments for children's development and learning that results in experiences that make them acquire the skills, characteristics, and values needed to stimulate self-actualization in childhood.

These approaches focus more on the possibilities than the problems. Positive design strives to create experiences that make children feel happy, encourages their curiosity, and inspires them to explore their world, their skills and talents; to support the establishment of certain virtues; to know their possibilities and limitations; to accept themselves as they are;

Figure 3. Room of multiple physical activities

to encourage creativity, mingled with the other characteristics that constitute the conditions needed to reach the level of self-actualization.

The most important point is that with the use of those design guidelines it is not necessary to come up with very complicated products. To promote creativity in children and a desire to explore, all that is needed is to develop very simple and flexible ideas (to let children imagine and explore different ways to use it and enjoy it). For example, toys to build as Lego, wooden blocks, a set of magnets, etc.; encourage children to create anything they want and imagine.

With the use of the tools and methodologies of positive design it is possible to develop products that stimulate children to have virtues and to become self-actualized adults, because it takes the knowledge from positive psychology that has studied healthy and flourishing people in order to establish patterns of behaviour, skills and virtues that facilitate the possibility of reaching a self-actualization lifestyle. Moreover, self-actualization as a term introduced by Maslow, who used positive psychology to define it, is totally correlated with the movement of positive design, which makes it easier to justify why those approaches could support self-actualization in children.

It is not possible to think that just with a product or an environment it is possible to give children the opportunity to acquire all the conditions needed to become self-actualized children. For that goal it is necessary that children have access to different ambiances in all the learning contexts that promote happiness, creativity, social contact, an understanding of the world, and the possibility to discover themselves. They also need different products like toys, musical instruments and educational tools, that support the conditions mentioned above.

To explore the opportunities that design could have to contribute in the self-actualization process of children, it is important to mention some specific values, described by Maslow, that are needed to become self-actualized:

- Truth, rather than dishonesty.
- Goodness, rather than evil.

Figure 4. Room sensory stimulation

- Beauty, not ugliness or vulgarity.
- Unity, wholeness, and transcendence of opposites, not arbitrariness or forced choices.
- Aliveness, not deadness or the mechanization of life.
- Uniqueness, not bland uniformity.
- Perfection and necessity, not sloppiness, inconsistency, or accident.
- Completion, rather than incompleteness.
- Justice and order, not injustice and lawlessness.
- Simplicity, not unnecessary complexity.
- Richness, not environmental impoverishment.
- Effortlessness, not strain.
- Playfulness, not grim, humourless, drudgery.
- Self-sufficiency, not dependency.
- Meaningfulness, rather than senselessness.

With the use of the concepts of positive design, and while taking some of the values mentioned above, design could be used as a means to support the values in learning environments giving children the opportunity to have positive experiences, for example:

- Designing games and toys to let children experience the reward obtained when you are honest, with truth you can win. For example, in this point it could be possible to design objects with action-reaction that when children make the right selection, the reaction or feedback from the toy is a reward for them.
- Designing elements to create a theatre, customs, and objects to build different scenarios. With the participation of teachers, children create and represent stories that teach them that when people act evilly, they receive a punishment and are unhappy. It could also be very interesting if children could participate in building the scenarios and creating the customs with guidance, to let them use their imagination and make it tangible.

Figure 5. Music room

- Designing educative objects or toys, to learn in a playful way different concepts that are most of the time boring for children, to demonstrate that everything could be playful and is possible to enjoy while you learn.
- Designing simple play objects to teach children that it is not necessary to have very complex (or very technological) toys and elements to have fun and to be creative. Simplicity is better than complexity. For example, children can entertain themselves with clay and moulds by creating everything that they imagine.
- Designing objects that represent different things from daily living that children must learn to use independently, but which are adequate to their dimensions, and therefore promote exploration in their use, and to learn in a safe way to be self-sufficient in daily activities.
- Designing play objects that allow children to understand that they do not have to fear difference; every person is unique. For example, children that do not have contact with children with disabilities could feel afraid or curious about disability. However, if they have the opportunity to experience it through games they could understand that every individual has different skills and strengths. For example, a game with pirates, in which every player represents a disability (having a wood leg, or an eye patch), and employ different strengths in order to complete tasks.

As the examples mentioned above, positive design, its tools and methodologies, could be used to design learning environments, objects, as well as strategies to support, stimulate, or encourage children to acquire values and skills that are needed in becoming self-actualized adults.

DISCUSSION

Design is about exploring all the possibilities that exist to communicate an intention through the use and experience of products and/or environments. All the approaches mentioned

above give designers some guidelines to focus their efforts and creativity to develop products and/or environments with a goal: to stimulate or motivate children to become self-actualized people. Positive design especially has a lot of potential to support human values, lifestyles, and has a big correlation with self-actualization. Both come for the positive psychology movement, therefore both have the same foundations and principles.

To ensure that children become self-actualized adults, there are different skills, characteristics and values they must gain during their development and growth. In the literature it is possible to find evidence supporting the fact that it is probable to encourage children to be self-actualized human-beings through appropriate stimulus to ensure good development in all the areas and education as a mean, and as an environment to let them explore, learn, and improve their skills and abilities.

The education environment should encourage kids to be creative, know their abilities and talents, give them the opportunity to discover what they like and want, to choose, decide, and fail themselves. Facing failure is really important to make them adults with a tolerance to failure, 'Experts are thus people who have failed many times' (Burlleson, 2005), making them look for more answers and solutions, always searching for a growth in knowledge.

CONCLUSIONS

Taking into account the different perspectives and fields consulted to write this paper, the most important finding is that it is possible to stimulate self-actualization in children applying different methodologies, strategies, and approaches from the design field. Obviously since children's well-being and development also depends on adults around them, it could not be totally assured that just the design of environments and/or products will motivate and support self-actualization. Design is only one of the possible means to achieve this aim.

Designers need to be aware about the influence they can have on someone's life, to apply correctly all the possibilities and tools that exist in this field to obtain products, environments, services and, especially, experiences that support and promote, in this case, the pursuit of self-actualization since childhood.

The findings and connections made in the literature review suggest that design is more than just a knowledgeable area that creates products based on problems, it is also possible to design products or environments that give users positive experiences that, which make them happy. In the case of children, even to help them to become better adults, and with a greater chance of reaching the self-actualization level in their lives. According to the results it is necessary to undertake further research in the field of design for self-actualization, because there is evidence from the psychology and education areas that suggest it is possible to reach this goal.

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CRAFTSMANSHIP PRECEPTS FOR DESIGN PRACTICE

Ana Luiza Cerqueira Freitas
Universidade do Estado de Minas Gerais
✉ analu.cf@terra.com.br,
Lucas Monteiro Rocha Faria
Universidade do Estado de Minas Gerais
✉ lucasrochafaria@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The article proposes a reflection on the designer's position as a producer of objects and an agent that modifies the environment in which we live. We begin with an overview of the present state of the profession, in which the designer is most of the time bound to the framework of industrial production and has little autonomy in what concerns the product of his work. What we seek to understand is how the use of principles inherent to the way of life and work of craftsmen, as conceptualized by two North American thinkers, Charles Wright Mills and Richard Sennett, may contribute to recovering autonomy, thus endowing designers with a more critical and independent character.

The text here presented for reflection is a result from the research project 'Traditional craft techniques in Minas Gerais, Brazil', that took place at the School of Design of the University of Minas Gerais through Program Institutional Grants for Scientific Initiation — PIBIC/UEMG/FAPEMIG — Foundation for Research Support of Minas Gerais, notice number 06/2012.

KEYWORDS: *craftsmanship, craftsman, designer, production, craft of experience.*

INTRODUCTION

The convergence between design and crafts-based productive activities has produced a great number of papers in the institutional sphere. In Brazilian entities such as the Serviço de Apoio às Micro e Pequenas Empresas – SEBRAE (PROGRAMA SEBRAE DE ARTESANATO, 2004; FREITAS, COSTA e MENEZES, 2009), Serviço Nacional de Aprendizagem Rural – SENAR (2012), Empresa de Assistência Técnica e Extensão Rural — EMATER (Miranda, 2009), Programa do Artesanato Brasileiro — PAB, among others, as well as in the academic sphere, where the number of works is high. For instance, in the annals of the Brazilian Congress of Research and Development (Congresso Brasileiro de Pesquisa e Desenvolvimento em Design – P&D Design) (biennial national event) held in 2012, out of 700 presentations given as complete papers, round tables, and poster presentations, roughly 100 titles dealt with the relation between Design and Crafts.

A lot has been published about and invested in bringing design and crafts together, especially on occasions when the designer acts as a consultant, facilitating the creation, development, and improvement of crafted products, and, sometimes, of their respective productive processes. This is a practice that has been growing stronger in Brazil, making great works

and partnerships possible. But thinking the other way around, what do craftwork and, more precisely, the craftsman have to teach designers? What can designers learn from them?

Designers, just as everyone else, live a 'consuming life' where happenings flow and nothing is ever completely established (Bauman, 2001). However designers have more responsibility, for they are producers, as well as consumers, and therefore can develop new ideas to transform their environment. In present times we see an instrumentalization of the designer's profession; an alienation from the productive intention, subdued by economic interests. Design thus loses its autonomy, and its creative potential while instead having to come up with solutions in an ever more complex world (Mills, 2008).

In this article, based on works of two North American thinkers, Charles Wright Mills and Richard Sennett, we deal with how designers can take on a more active role by revisiting concepts extracted from craftsmanship.

THE DESIGNER AND TIME

We live in a time when everything moves so fast that it does not become established, a time when things are born already doomed to death, be it technical, cultural or symbolic. At first

sight one might think that in such a context, in which consumption is higher than ever before, the designer, the professional that shapes new objects (for consumption) has never been better. However, we must notice that, behind such consumerism and fast emergence of new products, there is a professional who has been gradually losing his autonomy — a process that starts with the Industrial Revolution (the Arts and Crafts Movement being a symbol of resistance).

Today design and, as a consequence, designers became a tool for the industry to sell more. The latter are professionals specialized in manipulating signs to increase consumption. When we look at things from this perspective, the designer has been fulfilling his role — but should that be his only function? These authors we here do not think so. They argue that we need a more critical way of thinking about what we produce, and that there is an ethical question involved in launching products into the world. Among the problems inherent to design, Bernhard Bürdek (2005) corroborates the question, mentioning that ‘design should promote and communicate services, but also – pursued energetically enough – help to prevent products that are senseless’ (Burdek, 2005, p.16).

INTELLECTUAL CRAFTSMANSHIP AND THE CRAFTSMAN

Charles Wright Mills, an American sociologist of the twentieth century, was interested in craftsmen. He saw in their work a new way of thinking sociology, and tried to capture that concept for sociological research and development. Mills felt sociology should be applied in ways that resulted in something relevant for societal development, and created a concept called ‘intellectual craftsmanship’, in which he draws a parallel between the way of life and production of craftsmen, and the way a sociologist should develop his or her thought and research. To him, craftsmen have several applicable values, as if sociologists were also craftsmen, but craftsmen of thought, a kind of thought, as he would later define more clearly, that does not become separated from action — ‘making is thinking’ (Sennet, 2012).

In a conference for designers entitled ‘The man in the middle: the designer’, Mills gives his interpretation of the North American designer and the scenario in which that professional works, and then explains what characterizes craftsmanship, drawing a parallel with design. Mills (2008, p.173) starts by saying that the designer has become an important part of economy, in which ‘his art is a business’, and where a certain development brought ‘art, science and learning into subordinate relation with the dominant institutions of the capitalist economy’. Because the productive capacity is much higher than demand, marketing techniques were developed that, combined with goods that wear out quickly, aim at keeping consumption always in expansion. In the authors’ view, there are three types of obsolescence,

- (1) technological, as when something wears out or something better is produced;
- (2) artificial, as when something is deliber-

ately designed so that it *will* wear out; and (3) status obsolescence, as when fashions are created in such ways that consumption brings disgrace or prestige in accordance with last year’s or this year’s model, and alongside the old struggle for existence, there is added the panic for status (Mills, 2008, p.177).

All that began in the 1920s, when production sped up considerably and supply became higher than demand, which led to the development of strategies for consumption to go on. The trend has only gotten worse now that the economy seems to be endlessly expanding. Among the three types described above, the third is the one where the designer has the greatest relevance, for ‘his economic task is to sell’ (Mills, 2008, p.177); his autonomy and intellectual capacity of critical thinking are subdued to the motto ‘God is the Big Sell’ (Mills, 2008, p.177), and he joins the company of other professionals who specialize in sales (advertisers, public relations, market researchers), whose goal is ‘less to make better products than to make products sell better’ (Mills, 2008, p.177).

There is a huge intellectual waste in looking for projects to deceive the customer and give him the impression of buying a sensation, status, and not the product itself. Designers themselves fall prey to such manipulation, as the market looks out for stars to add value to products, so that, becoming a star, a designer becomes a prisoner of his own success, and even if he gets tired of his style the demand for it forces him to keep it, in order to keep his status. On the other hand the situation is cruel for the rest of the population of designers, for ‘One is a smash hit or one is among the failures who are not produced; one is a best seller or one is among the hacks and failures; one is either absolutely tops or one is just nothing at all’ (Mills, 2008, p.179). Then if the designer does not fit into this system in order to reach the ideal standards established by the market, the latter demotes him. Living thus becomes a form of resistance or accommodation.

To wrap up the production frame in which designers work, the author emphasizes the fact that producers (designers, advertisement creators, people who conceive new objects) say ‘we only give them what they want’ (Mills, 2008, p.179). That is a deception that traps not only costumers, but also the people making consumption objects. Society’s need is totally shaped to this or that product, ‘consumers are trained to “want” that to which they are most continually exposed’ (Mills, 2008, p.179).

There is no relevant evolution in the vast majority of products justifying their being thrown away so easily. Thus all the commercial apparatus is mobilized to create a desire for a determinate product which is ‘newer’, and therefore ‘more beautiful’ than the previous. The shorter the life cycle of a product is, the better it is to keep that movement, which alienates and is in a sense cruel to people (most) who cannot keep up with the changes and get frustrated because of it. The designer plays a fundamental role in this context, manipulating signs, stirring people’s desire.

So, for the designer to break away from that cycle and look for a less alienating type of production, which contributes to the development of culture and the improvement of the space in which we live, Mills proposes that he rethinks the

way of modifying not only himself, but also the environment where he lives, because the designer 'is a creator and a critic of the physical frame of private and public life' (Mills, 2008, p.181). Craftsmanship is the way to do it; not only as an ideal, but also as a practice. Explaining what he understands as craftsmanship, the author lists five points.

The first and the second are related to freedom in work, for 'in craftsmanship there is no ulterior motive for work other than the product being made and the process of its creation' (Mills, 2008, p.181). Things are made for personal satisfaction, even if it lies in the satisfaction of another, the craftsman does not dissociate from the product of his work, he is always thinking about it, in its development, in the process and the final piece. The aesthetic experience that can be apprehended in the creation of those objects is transported to users, for 'in an impersonal, scheduled, a machined world, they (crafted objects) represent the personal and the spontaneous. They are the opposite of the stereotyped and the banalized' (Mills, 2008, p.181). The plan and the execution of work do not dissociate, and 'the craftsman is master of the activity and of himself in the process' (Mills, 2008, p.182). There is freedom in the execution of work, carried out according to personal preferences and experiences, and the craftsman is also free if he wants to change something during the process, which is conscious because the process is mastered as a whole, through conception, planning and execution: 'Work is a rational sphere of independent action' (Mills, 2008, p.182). The craftsman changes the way he works during the process of execution thinking of the meta-image he has in mind, so that he imagines all ways and mechanisms to reach the closest result to that image, and as the product materializes such process goes on, in the search of the best way to come to the desired result.

The third and fourth points deal with how work contributes to self-development, and how the relationship with work is contained in the craftsman's relationship with life. As techniques improve, so does thought, and vice versa. When he carries out his work, the craftsman is going through meaningful experiences, and when work stops for a moment, he is not interrupting the experience, but catching his breath to keep going. Creative and productive experience is so ingrained in the craftsman's life context that he does not disconnect himself from his activity as a craftsman when engaged in other activities. The same happens, or should happen, according to Mills, with designers.

In the fifth and last point the author emphasizes the importance of people who feed those ideas, for 'Such an independent stratum of craftsmen cannot flourish unless there are publics who support individuals who may not turn out to be first-rate' (Mills, 2008, p.182).

There is a restriction in the scenario we live, where the model makes decisions to be determined by the economic character, often limiting the designer's responsibility and critical thinking. That question is discussed by Richard Sennett, another North American sociologist, posterior to Mills, in the beginning of his book *The Craftsman*. He quotes a sentence from his professor and supervisor Hannah Arendt to sum up that initial situation: 'people who make things usually don't

understand what they are doing' (Sennett, 2008, p.1), and, he adds, take 'the work as an end in itself' (Sennett, 2008, p.6), thus raising the discussion of the relation between technique and thought in which one questions the responsibility that befalls (or not) people who develop and create new things. It would then be necessary to think of things before effectively building them, and predict the impacts they might have, both the benefits and harms. Sennett quotes the inventor of the atomic bomb, among others, to illustrate the idea that people seek development on its own, without critically thinking about the relevance of what they are doing, and leaving political and economic decisions to guide development. When that happens, those interests may not converge into ethical attitudes and may end up producing catastrophic results.

Designers have been suffering from apathy and passively wait for the industry to set the guidelines for configuring new objects. A wider critical view of the implications of what is being developed, so that by solving a problem we do not create a bigger one. Such as Sennett suggests, the philosopher Flusser (2008) formulates the question, stating that often, or even all the time, we remove obstacles by placing other obstacles in the way. That is, when we do not think about what we are doing, we simply allow more obstacles to get in our way. However, when we assume the attitude of craftsmen trying to master the totality of our acts we can develop relevant things.

Craftsmen's knowledge was built through the sharing of skills among people, as well as by passing them down to the following generations. The formation of craftsmen happened through others' knowledge, 'personal genius had little meaning in this context' (Sennett, 2008, p.22). Mills' idea, presented in the beginning, might sound idealistic, but Sennett believes that open source software, such as Linux, is an excellent example of the application of elements typical of craftsmen; for information is totally shared and the search for improvement is constant.

A community of craftsmen (...) is focused on achieving quality, on doing good work, which is the craftsman's primordial mark of identity. In the traditional world of the archaic potter or doctor, standards for good work were set by the community, as skills passed down from generation to generation (Sennett, 2008, p.25).

There is impersonality of work, and, on the other hand, no predominant intention driving the development, except getting to improve the program at each new version. In design there is the idea of *open design*, where creations are shared, not only by other designers, but also by people, potential customers who want to give their opinion about the subject. However, we do not see the same degree of sharing here as in the creation of open source software.

Sennett stresses the importance of repetition for learning, and how that was lost with the advent of new technologies. There is today a distance between head and hand, the opposite of the fundamental characteristic of all craftsmanship. CAD tools, which are extremely important for the modern world, such proximity is reduced, for example, by CAD tools, but they also limit thought, once they do not allow one to 'do it, (...) redo it, and (...) redo it again' (Renzo Piano, quoted by

Sennett, 2008, p.40). The speed at which a mistake is corrected makes its comprehension impossible, thus preempting the concept of repetition, as explored by Walter Benjamin (1992) in his text 'One way Street'. As Benjamin writes, there is a very big difference between flying over a road and walking on it; that is, the view that one has when one must get close to the object by repetition is much richer, and the process of repetition allows that. Benjamin mentions the example of Chinese copiers: 'Only the copied text thus commands the soul of him who is occupied with it, whereas the mere reader never discovers the new aspects of his inner self that are opened by the text...' (Benjamin, 1979, p. 50). Another great limitation of CAD tools is the exactness of algorithms, which cannot allow for all conceivable possibilities; even if they get very good, we will be limited to an interface that responds to commands that are not our own.

THE DESIGNER AS A CRAFTSMAN

The concepts introduced by the authors might be seen as a union of theory and practice, head and hand. By becoming also the producer of his creations the designer cannot only better develop his own ideas, but also apprehend the process. And once he is shaping something he imagined, to which he can give his enthusiasm and dedication, the designer works harder, and gains relevant experience of his trade. There is today a distance between the people who think the world and the people who make and build this world — a distance between art and technique. The designer might play a fundamental role in this situation, as a professional who can work in that interface, bringing both elements closer. Art and technique are sometimes seen as opposites, but, when brought together, they can contribute to improve our experience of the world, insofar as one thinks about objects as possibilities, as ways to interact with others, and to stimulate increased understanding and cooperation among people.

Both Mills and Sennett emphasize the importance of strengthening that relation to create a greater connection with work. The pragmatist current of thought to which Sennett belongs emphasizes that 'to work well people need freedom from means-ends relationships' (Sennett, 2008, p.288), and in order to get that we must understand 'the value of experience understood as a craft' (Sennett, 2008, p.288), where the trade of producing material things gives one a better understanding of others; once 'the craft of making things provides insight into the techniques of experience that can shape our dealings with others' (Sennett, 2008, p.289).

There are great challenges to be overcome, once the current model asserts itself, and the social value given to the craftsman (and the designer) is low. There is a conflict between nature and culture; the natural productive action of craftsmen opposes the current cultural apparatus. An improvement in that apparatus is needed so that no conflict between them arises. For the designer to work according to crafts precepts, beyond his will, a greater interest is needed, a support, as Mills claims.

Today we can be anywhere through the Internet, and the circulation of new ideas is easier. With tools like crowd funding those ideas become viable without the support of any big companies. In such initiatives there are crafts precepts, such as reciprocal cooperation, exchange of information, collective creation, organization in nets and communities; all of those listed by Sennett (2008). The main objective is not economic. As we can see in Saramago's *The Cave*, for a craftsman his trade is not solely about making a living; even if he wants to do something else, he cannot, he cannot work if not with that; what he experiences there is so pleasant and motivating that he cannot think of anything else. There is pride in what he is doing, in the work of his hands (and head). That is what designers (and all other producers) are able to feel when they experience those concepts.

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PLEASANTNESS AND AROUSAL IN TWENTY-FIVE POSITIVE EMOTIONS ELICITED BY DURABLE PRODUCTS

Juan Carlos Ortíz Nicolás

Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Centro de Investigaciones de Diseño Industrial

✉ juancarlos.ortiz@cidi.unam.mx

Marco Aurisicchio

Imperial College London, Department of Mechanical Engineering

✉ m.aurisicchio@imperial.ac.uk

Pieter M.A. Desmet

Delft University of Technology, Faculty of Industrial Design Engineering

✉ P.M.A.Desmet@tudelft.nl

ABSTRACT

This study reports quantitative research into two basic dimensions of emotions: pleasantness and arousal. Fifty-nine participants evaluated these two dimensions for a set of twenty-five positive emotions in relation to human-product interactions. Three levels of arousal were identified: 'exciting', 'median' and 'calm'. Nine emotions were found to be exciting, namely energetic, euphoria, amusement, desire, joy, love, inspiration, lust and surprise. Ten emotions were found to be median in arousal, namely fascination, satisfaction, confidence, pride, anticipation, enchantment, courage, hope, worship and admiration. Six emotions were found to be calm, namely relaxation, relief, kindness, dreaminess, respect and sympathy. Three levels of pleasantness were also identified: 'very pleasant', 'mildly pleasant' and 'pleasant'. Six emotions were found to be very pleasant, namely amusement, joy, satisfaction, inspiration, euphoria and love. Thirteen emotions were found to be mildly pleasant, namely relief, relaxation, kindness, dreaminess, confidence, fascination, pride, enchantment, anticipation, energetic, desire, lust and surprise. Finally six emotions were found to be pleasant, namely respect, sympathy, admiration, courage, hope and worship. The results of this study can guide designers to define the emotional tone of the user experience that they are aiming for.

KEYWORDS: *design for emotions, pleasantness, arousal, positive emotions, user experience.*

INTRODUCTION

In the field of psychology scholars tend to agree that emotions involve various dimensions or modalities (Scherer, 2005; Frijda, 1986; Russell, 2003; Roseman and Smith, 2001). Expression, bodily arousal and subjective experience are examples of these (Scherer, 2005). In particular, two dimensions that have captured scholars' attention are pleasantness and arousal. Pleasantness characterises the hedonic valence of an emotion and arousal its bodily symptoms. Thus, emotions are pleasant or unpleasant as well as calm or exciting. Based on the idea that all affective states arise from these two dimensions, Russell (2003) captured these affective states through the concept of *core affect*, which has also been used to explain user experience (Desmet and Hekkert, 2007). Pleasure and arousal have also led to the development of tools to measure human emotions, which have been adopted in general affective research (Lang, 1980) as well as in user experience research (Isbister, et al., 2007; Vastenburg et al., 2011; Laurans

et al., 2012; Desmet, 2002). For example, the self-assessment manikin, known as the SAM method, is a tool based on a series of human cartoons that are used to measure, among others, pleasantness and arousal (Lang, 1980). It is important to consider pleasantness and arousal in emotional design because emotions can lead to different behavioural consequences (Frijda, 1986; Laros et al., 2005) and these dimensions are descriptive of the associated behavioural states. Designers, for instance, can reflect on whether a product or service should be designed to elicit feelings of relaxation or inspiration. Both relaxed and inspired people may feel good during human-product interaction. However, the behavioural reactions involved are different, as relaxed people become inactive and withdrawn (state of low arousal), while inspired people become more active (state of high arousal) and are stimulated to create something out of their inspiration (Desmet, 2012; Ortiz Nicolás, 2014). Research has shown that design decisions can be taken to stimulate one of these states. For example, it has been documented that arousal can be increased in stores if they are designed using warm colours (Kueller and Mikkelsen

lides, 1993) and fast tempo music (Holbrook and Gardner, 1993). In the field of product design the use of colour and the type of interaction can be linked to decisions that enhance a low or high arousal experience. Arousal is also relevant because intense (i.e. high arousal) emotions were perceived by a group of designers to be more difficult to design for (Ortíz Nicolás, et al., 2013). Pleasantness is also influential for user experience because all experiences have some kind of feeling-tone that may be classified as pleasant, unpleasant, or neutral, a response that is regulated by human emotions (Varela et al., 1991). Thus, emotions colour experience (McCarthy and Wright, 2004) and the hue depends on the involved pleasantness and arousal.

Pleasure is an element that in recent years has received significant attention in research into user experience (e.g. Jordan, 2000). Pleasure is generally considered to be the most abstract and superordinate dimension of an emotional experience (Laros et al., 2005). Research into consumer behaviour has shown the benefits of studying pleasure at a subordinate level based on basic (Laros et al., 2005) and complex (Richins, 1997) emotions. The results of this research indicate that a focus on basic emotions has greater explanatory power than an emphasis on the superordinate dimension, i.e. pleasure (Laros et al., 2005). Following a similar line of thought, scholars in the field of user experience have reported that pleasure is an umbrella term and as a result is too general to understand or to design for (Desmet, 2012). To overcome this limitation the term has been deconstructed. Research has, in fact, identified a set of twenty-five positive emotions that are relevant for product design and pleasant experiences (Desmet, 2012). This work has constituted an important step towards a better understanding of pleasure in user experience. However, it does not provide a detailed analysis of the emotions in terms of arousal and pleasantness.

Building on the view that pleasantness and arousal are two basic dimensions of emotions that have not been studied in depth in previous research, the aim of this study is to investigate the nuances of pleasantness and arousal in twenty-five positive emotions experienced in response to durable products. There is a need to develop knowledge relevant to the field of product design because emotional experiences in human-product interactions are different from those gained in human-human interactions (McCarthy and Wright, 2004). For example, the joy of solving a task cannot be assumed to be the same as the joy of requited love and the frustration caused by an unresponsive partner is not the same as the frustration caused by an unresponsive computer (McCarthy and Wright, 2004). The latter indicates that pleasure and arousal vary in human-product interactions.

PRODUCTS AND EMOTIONS

It is well established that products elicit emotional responses (Frijda, 1986; Desmet, 2002; Norman 2004). However, some emotions are experienced more often than others in human-product interaction. To identify those emotions, Desmet

(2002) assembled a list of positive and negative emotions on the basis of studies carried out in the field of psychology. Using questionnaire research, he determined which of these emotions are most frequently triggered by products. A challenge of this approach, however, is that it relies on the participants' ability to recall previous experiences. To overcome this issue, Desmet used collages showing products from different categories to stimulate participants' recall regarding emotional experiences. A similar study involving the employment of collages and a list of emotions was carried out by Ortíz Nicolás and Hernández López (2008) to identify product-relevant emotions in a new cultural context. More recently, Desmet (2012) reported the use of six collages to identify positive emotions evoked by products. In this study, however, Desmet indicated that the collages were used to give participants an idea of the possibilities that they might consider instead of serving merely as a recall tool. In conclusion, all these studies started with pre-defined lists of emotions, which were presented to users through questionnaires, and all employed collages to stimulate their recall.

UNDERSTANDING TWO DIMENSIONS OF TWENTY FIVE POSITIVE EMOTIONS

This section presents the process followed to carry out this study, including the research approach, participants, materials and procedure.

Research approach

As discussed above, previous studies have investigated user emotions using questionnaires and collages. Building on this work, this research relies on the use of a questionnaire to identify the pleasantness and arousal of an emotion set. The main difference between this research and previous work is that it aims to investigate nuances of pleasantness and arousal in twenty-five positive emotions when experienced in response to durable products, rather than their relevance to product design, which has already been identified in (Desmet, 2012; Ortíz Nicolás and Hernández López, 2008; Desmet, 2002).

Research in the field of psychology has traditionally used bipolar dimensions to examine both pleasantness and arousal (Russell, 2003; Scherer, 2005). For example, it has employed a bipolar descriptor for pleasantness such as pleasant-unpleasant (Scherer, 2005). This study, instead, because of its focus on positive emotions, has employed a monopolar descriptor for pleasantness such as pleasant-very pleasant. For arousal, in contrast, it has relied on a traditional bipolar descriptor such as calm-excited because this dimension does not have a negative connotation.

Respondents

Fifty-nine respondents participated to the study (37 males and 22 females). The number of respondents was determined by

referring to figures used in previous comparable studies (see Desmet, 2002; Ortíz Nicolás and Hernández López, 2008) and the requirement to compute a statistical analysis. The respondents were of various nationalities, French and British being the two commonest. Participants had no relation to the fields of product or industrial design. Most were students enrolled at Imperial College London. Forty-five were undergraduate students, seven were postgraduates and the remaining seven were professionals. Participants were aged between 19 and 39 (mean = 23.73; SD = 5.47). Eleven were native English speakers and the others had a good command of the language.

Material

The material used in the study included a questionnaire, a set of instructions, and five collages.

A two-part questionnaire was developed. In the first part participants answered demographic questions, about age, gender, and background. In the second part, participants rated twenty-five positive emotions in relation to pleasantness (from '1 = pleasant' to '5 = very pleasant') and arousal (from '1 = calm' to '9 = excited'). The emotions used in this research are: admiration, amusement, anticipation, confidence, courage, desire, dreaminess, enchanted, energetic, euphoria, fascination, hope, inspiration, joy, kindness, love, lust, pride, relaxed, relief, respect, satisfaction, surprise, sympathy, and worship. These emotions were identified by Desmet (2012) based on their relevance to human-product interactions. Three versions of the questionnaire were generated with the emotions appearing in randomised order.

Written instructions were developed to clarify the concepts of pleasantness and arousal for participants, which were presented to them on sheets of A4 paper. The complete instructions can be found in Ortíz Nicolás (2014). Five collages depicting a large variety of daily used products were employed. These were borrowed from a previous study (Desmet, 2012). The collages were printed out in high quality colour on A3 paper, see Figure 1.

Figure 1. An example of one of the collages that was used to stimulate participants' recall

Procedure

First, participants were informed that the focus of the study was on positive emotions and durable products, which were defined for them as manufactured items that are expected to have a relatively long useful life, e.g. a bike, a kettle or a digital camera. Second, participants received five collages intended to stimulate their memory; they were allowed to look at them for approximately 30 seconds each. A similar time was used in previous studies. Third, participants received written instructions on how to fill in the questionnaire, in which the concepts of pleasantness and arousal were explained. Respondents were also informed that they could cross out the emotions that they felt were not provoked by durable products. Participants took an average of 15 minutes to complete the questionnaire. The procedure was carried out individually in a quiet room.

EMOTION NAME	N	Pleasant		Arousal		NPE: Exclusion
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Joy	59	4.56	0.73	6.47	1.58	0
Love	52	4.42	0.82	6.35	1.93	6
Satisfaction	59	4.27	0.98	5.02	2.20	0
Amusement	59	4.19	0.90	6.85	1.46	0
Euphoria	58	4.19	1.08	7.31	1.89	1
Inspiration	59	4.15	0.94	6.29	1.97	0
Energetic	58	3.97	1.23	7.69	1.50	1
Confidence	59	3.97	1.00	4.98	2.00	0
Desire	59	3.86	1.01	7.00	1.58	0
Fascination	58	3.79	0.87	5.69	1.88	1
Relaxation	59	3.66	1.29	2.68	2.10	0
Relief	59	3.73	1.19	3.63	2.02	0
Lust	50	3.58	1.20	7.04	1.97	9
Kindness	53	3.57	1.14	3.87	1.90	6
Pride	59	3.42	1.13	5.02	2.19	0
Enchantment	58	3.31	1.33	4.95	2.40	1
dreaminess	59	3.24	1.28	3.10	2.47	0
Surprise	58	3.19	1.25	6.28	1.99	1
Anticipation	59	3.12	1.27	6.02	2.04	0
Courage	58	2.93	1.30	5.66	2.28	0
Admiration	59	2.90	1.12	4.36	1.94	1
Hope	59	2.78	1.35	4.95	1.92	0
Worship	44	2.76	1.38	4.64	2.53	15
Respect	53	2.64	1.39	3.15	1.89	6
Sympathy	48	2.63	1.38	3.08	2.07	11

Table 1. Pleasantness and arousal of emotions (No: Number of responses; M: mean; SD: standard deviation; NPE: Number of participants who excluded the emotion)

Figure 2. Pleasantness and arousal of the emotions

Results

This section first presents the results for pleasantness and arousal of emotions and second the emotions that participants indicated as not being provoked by durable products. The pleasantness and arousal of the emotions are displayed in Table 1.

To further explore these differences, emotions were plotted on a two-dimensional diagram (Figure 2) with pleasantness as the vertical and arousal as the horizontal axis. For ease of interpretation, seven ‘positive emotion domains’ are visualised in the graphical plot with three levels of arousal: calm, median, and exciting (from 1 to 9) and three levels of pleasantness: pleasant, mildly pleasant and very pleasant (from 1 to 5). These levels combine to create nine positive emotion domains, which are each briefly described below.

Domain A: Median arousal - very pleasant emotions

One emotion was found to be more or less exciting and very pleasant, namely satisfaction.

Domain B: Exciting - very pleasant emotions

Five emotions were found to be exciting and very pleasant, namely joy, love, amusement, inspiration, and euphoria.

Domain C: calm - mildly pleasant emotions

Four emotions were found to be calm and mildly pleasant, namely relief, relaxed, kindness, and dreamy.

Domain D: Median arousal - mildly pleasant emotions

Five emotions were found to be median in arousal and mildly pleasant, namely confidence, fascination, pride, enchantment and anticipation.

Domain E: Exciting - mildly pleasant emotions

Four emotions were found to be exciting and mildly pleasant, namely energetic, desire, lust and surprise.

Domain F: calm - pleasant emotions

Two emotions were found to be calm and pleasant, namely respect and sympathy.

Domain G: Median arousal - pleasant emotions

Finally, four emotions were found to be median arousal and pleasant, namely admiration, courage, hope and worship.

As can be seen in Figure 2, the additional two domains “excited - pleasant” and “calm and very pleasant” do not contain emotions.

The last aspect to report is that nineteen participants (32% of the total) removed at least one emotion, indicating that they did not experience certain emotions in relation to durable products. The emotions that were most frequently crossed out were as follows: worship (25%), sympathy (19%), lust (15%), love (12%), kindness (10%) and respect (10%).

DISCUSSION

The aim of this study was to investigate the pleasantness and arousal of twenty-five positive emotions. As indicated in the introduction, pleasure is the most abstract and superordinate dimension of emotions (Laros et al., 2005); and it is also an umbrella term that is too general and difficult to design for (Desmet, 2012). The results of this study show that emotions elicited in human-product interactions are pleasant, mildly pleasant and very pleasant, a finding that calls for further research in order to deconstruct the term pleasure (Laros et al., 2005; Desmet, 2012). In addition, it was possible to identify that with respect to arousal, emotions are exciting, median and calm. Figure 2 introduced seven positive emotion domains. It is interesting to note that the domains “excited and pleasant” and “calm and very pleasant” do not contain

emotions. These domains are at the opposite extremes of the three levels of pleasantness or arousal. This indicates that, in general, calm positive emotions may not be perceived as the most pleasant positive emotions and, likewise, that moderately pleasant emotions may not be perceived as the most exciting. It is important to consider, however, that the domains in Figure 2 do not represent fixed classes of emotion because they were defined by the authors.

Pleasantness

Differences in pleasure in user experience are to some extent implied in previous research into user experience, e.g. in terms of the sources that stimulate pleasure, i.e. physical, psychological, ideological and social (Jordan, 2000), and specific product attributes that enhance pleasure (Burns and Evans 2000; Porter et al., 2008). It is possible that the emotions experienced during pleasant experiences will enable scholars to develop a detailed account of those differences. The latter is suggested because it is well-established that there are differences in the experience of positive emotions (Scherer, 2005; Frijda, 1986; Russell, 2003; Roseman and Smith, 2001). For example, the emotion joy creates the urge to play and be playful, encompassing not only physical and social play, but also intellectual and artistic play (Fredrickson, 1998). The latter behavioural reactions can hardly be associated with satisfaction, which is frequently experienced with products when they work well (Desmet, 2012; Ortíz Nicolás et al., 2013). The results of this study indicate that satisfaction is a very pleasant emotion. The experience of satisfaction, as very pleasant, explains to some extent the findings of Burns and Evans (2000), who reported that when executed well the basic functionality of a product is a source of pleasure. This pleasure, however, may never be able to put a smile on the face of the user, as argued by Hassenzahl (2010). This is because research on emotions indicates that satisfaction cannot stimulate a behavioural reaction such as smiling. Putting a smile on the user's face may be achieved by focusing on other factors such as user aspirations, self-image, values and needs (Jordan, 2000). It may also be achieved by focusing on emotions such as joy or amusement, which might stimulate a behavioural reaction such as a smile. It may, therefore, be concluded that the pleasure gain from a product design based on satisfaction is different from a design based on joy.

Research in user experience has also suggested different types of experiences (e.g. Hassenzahl et al., 2010; Ortiz Nicolas et al., 2013a). For example, two types of pleasant experiences identified as a result of interacting with great products are significant and pragmatic. The latter is based on excellent instrumental performance and the former on the significant role that the product has in users' lives (Ortiz Nicolas et al., 2013a). Interestingly, the emotions involved in each of these two experiences vary. In the pragmatic experience the most frequently felt emotions were satisfaction, relaxation and amusement; for the significant experience, by contrast, the most frequently felt emotions were joy, satisfaction, relaxation, confidence,

inspiration and pride (Ortiz Nicolas et al., 2013a). These findings are in line with the idea that focusing on emotions has greater explanatory power than the superordinate dimension, i.e. pleasure (Laros et al., 2006; Desmet, 2012).

Other aspects that may explain the differences between emotions in terms of pleasure are reported next. It has been identified that some emotions, such as joy or pride, stimulate well-being (Ellsworth and Smith, 1988; Fredrickson, 2003). The agency of pleasure may also explain the differences between the pleasantness of emotions, i.e. those assigned to the self may be more pleasant than those triggered by external agents. For instance, confidence may be more pleasant than respect because when experiencing it the person feels that he or she is in control. This indicates that solutions that shift from products to people seem to be experienced more pleasantly.

Arousal

A fundamental difference between emotions resides in the way in which they are felt, i.e. exciting, median arousal, and calm (Russell, 2003; Scherer, 2005; Varela et al., 1991). For instance, exciting emotions are clearly distinctive because high arousal makes people notice them. The results of this study show that the set of twenty-five positive emotions includes fewer calm emotions than exciting and median arousal. This may be explained by taking into account the findings of research on emotions, which have suggested that there are more negative basic emotions than positive ones (see a comparison of views in Ortony and Turner, 1990) and that basic emotions tend to be exciting, e.g. anger, fear, anxiety, joy, and happiness. The latter finding may indicate that human beings have developed a richer language to describe exciting states in comparison to calm states. It would be interesting to study calm experiences provoked by products in detail, in order to identify if there is a similar richness of experienced emotions as in exciting experiences. It is also expected that exciting experiences caused by interaction with products should elicit specific emotions, i.e. high in arousal.

Design implications

Previous research into arousal has identified specific attributes that designers should implement in the design of products if arousal is to be stimulated, i.e. warm colours (Kueller and Mikkellides, 1993). The results of this study offer designers the option of focusing on emotions that are high or low in arousal when they are attempting to design an exciting or calm experience. This broadens design opportunities, because emotions are elicited by at least the following aspects: product, interaction, the meaning of the product, activity, the self, and others (Desmet, 2012). Designers could, for instance, focus on particular activities that enhance relaxation instead of just focusing on specific colours.

Research in the field of consumer behaviour has also shown that designers should consider the manipulation of arousal in stores based on consumer motivations. When consumers

are motivated by recreation, high arousal has a positive effect on pleasantness. However, when consumers have a task-oriented motivation, high arousal decreases pleasantness (Kaltcheva et al., 2006). As was identified in this study the most pleasant emotions involve median and high arousal. This may not always be desirable, as previous research has identified. For instance, an excited experience is not appropriate for all product categories, e.g., to provide an obvious example, calm experiences may fit better in hospitals and exciting ones in amusement parks. Designers could use the results of this study to reflect on the level of arousal and pleasantness that the project at hand deserves. Based on this reflection designers could select the most appropriate emotions, which may directly impact on decisions concerning the configuration of the product. In conclusion, a fundamental issue that this study stimulates is the importance of seeking out and defining the appropriate emotional tone required of the design. Designers can consider occasions when moderately pleasant feelings are more appropriate than very pleasant feelings. The issues that will define which experience to design for, and how to determine a fitting target experience, remain to be investigated.

The results of this study build on a predefined set of twenty-five positive emotions (Desmet, 2012). Other characteristics of the set have also been investigated and can be found in Ortíz Nicolás et al., (2013) and Yoon et al., (2013). The overall aim of investigating positive emotions is to develop a robust source of knowledge that designers can rely upon. This study adds to that source of knowledge.

Limitations and future research

Even though this study used collages to diminish the biases of recalling emotions it is acknowledged that responding to a collage is not the same as interacting with actual products. Future research could reduce recall bias by using a set of products that users can actually see and interact with. Previous work has suggested that defining a product sample to study emotions is an alternative way to reduce recall bias (e.g. Hassenzahl, 2004; Ortíz Nicolás, and Hernández López, 2008; Ortíz Nicolás, 2014). It is important to report that studying pleasantness and arousal is not sufficient to capture further differences among the emotions studied (see also Ekman, 1999). A line of research suggested by this study is to explore whether a calm experience is less pleasant than an exciting one, as the findings of this study suggest. Finally, further research is required in order to understand the reasons why some participants in this research reported worship, sympathy, lust, love, kindness and respect as emotions that were not experienced in their interactions with products.

CONCLUSIONS

This study has presented empirical research that investigated a set of twenty-five positive emotions according to two dimensions i.e. pleasantness and arousal. For these positive emo-

tions, three basic levels of pleasantness were identified, namely *pleasant*, *mildly pleasant* and *very pleasant*, as well as three basic levels of arousal, namely *exciting*, *median* and *calm*.

This research builds upon previous work, which identified a set of twenty-five positive emotions that represent the repertoire of positive emotions that people may experience in human-product interaction. The contribution of this particular study concerns the investigation of two dimensions of emotions. At this stage, the knowledge developed through the study may be used by designers to inform the selection of some emotions over others, when aiming to control the level of pleasantness and arousal of an experience in the specific context of a design brief. It may also be used to choose emotions when developing tools to measure emotions elicited by products and to organise emotions based on arousal and pleasantness.

The methodological approach used in this study was useful to examine the pleasantness and arousal of twenty-five positive emotions. Based on the results we conclude that a pleasant-very pleasant and an exciting-calm scale capture basic differences between emotions. To gain deeper knowledge of the subtleties and nuances of the emotions, qualitative research methods may be an alternative. Investigating other qualities and dimensions of emotions, such as behavioural reactions and agency, is important to create more detailed profiles.

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IN THE EYE OF THE PATIENT INDIVIDUAL DIFFERENCES IN EMOTIONAL REACTIONS TO VISUAL DESIGN AESTHETICS OF HEALTH-CARE PRODUCTS

John Magnus Roos

Veryday

Centre for Consumer Science (CFK) and Department of Business and Administration,
School of Business Economics and Commercial Law, University of Gothenburg

✉ Magnus.roos@veryday.com, Magnus.roos@cfk.gu.se

In memory of Mikael Nevala

ABSTRACT

This study explores how the personality traits of potential patients influence their emotional reactions to the visual design aesthetics of health-care products. Sixty-six students completed a personality test and reported their emotional reactions to thirteen photos of health-care products. The key-findings were (1) a high degree of extraversion influences pleasant affect, (2) a high degree of neuroticism influences unpleasant affect, especially fear, (3) a low degree of conscientiousness influences pleasant affect in terms of positive surprise, (4) a high degree of openness influences happiness, (5) a high degree of extraversion influences fear, while a low degree of extraversion influences sadness (6) a low degree of extraversion, a low degree of neuroticism and/or a high degree of conscientiousness influence the absence of emotional reaction. The study explains why identical products evoke different emotions in different individuals, which is an important step in understanding how different design aesthetics satisfy different individuals based on their personalities.

KEYWORDS: *visceral design, aesthetics, basic emotions, appraisal, personality.*

INTRODUCTION

In today's world, emotional design plays an increasingly important role in creating desire for consumer goods and preferences for commercial messages, and has become a key-driver of consumer value and business value. Rather than goods that are purchased on a consumer market, this study has a somewhat different approach; it focuses on the emotions of people who are exposed to health-care products. The idea is that all of us can, and probably will, end up in a hospital and be exposed to a variety of products that we have not chosen.

Emotions are subjective and individuals differ in their emotional reaction to a given product (Desmet, 2008). It is the personal significance of a product, rather than the product itself, that causes the emotion. Different individuals who appraise the same product in different ways experience different emotions (Desmet, 2010). Personality theorists divide people along such traits as openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism. To designers,

this means that no single design will satisfy everyone (Norman, 2004). According to Lewis (2001), it is necessary to take a closer look at individual differences in order to better understand the development of emotions. The aim of this study is to explore if and how personality traits influence emotional reactions to health-care products.

The present study address the questions of whether and how personality traits can contribute to our understanding of emotions, and it discusses how such insights might be relevant for designers. Our theoretical model is based on an appraisal process of fast thinking, basic emotions and personality. Our ambition is to give some psychological contributions to design research, based not only on personality theories, but also on Ekman's 1982 framework of basic emotions and Kahneman's (2011) best seller "Thinking fast and slow." The empirical study and the data analysis are guided by this theoretical framework. The result will be discussed in terms of methodological limitations and related to multidisciplinary research (e.g. neuroscience, psychology, design and marketing) on personality traits and emotions.

AN APPRAISAL PROCESS OF THINKING FAST, BASIC EMOTIONS AND PERSONALITY

Thinking fast

The human brain seems to consist of three different levels, especially relevant for processing information. Firstly, the visceral level, which is automatic and fast. Secondly, the behavioral level, which controls everyday behavior. Thirdly, the reflective level, which is contemplative and thoughtful (Norman, 2004). Chupchik (1999) has a similar perspective and distinguishes between three levels of emotional meanings related to products: sensory/aesthetic, cognitive/behavioral and personal/symbolic. The first level represents sensory qualities that have an immediate effect on experience, the second represents meaning related to performance and ease of use, and the third represents personal meaning beyond product functions and appearance (Chupchik, 1999). Some researchers refer to emotions at the visceral level as “aesthetic” emotions because they are elicited by sensations that are pleasing or displeasing to our senses (Desmet, 2008; Lazarus, 1991). Aesthetic emotions are intrinsic feelings of pleasure or displeasure related to affect disposition, rather than higher-level cognitive processes. Overbeeke and Hekkert (1999) stated that many products or product categories have reached such a level of technical performance that they have become difficult to discriminate on a functional basis:

“Thus, when two coffee makers basically make the same pot of coffee, we take the one that gives us a pleasant, desirable, or inspired feeling” (Overbeeke & Hekkert, 1999, p. 5).

Whereas Norman (2004) argues that appraisal is only involved at the reflective level, Desmet (2008) argues that appraisal can be involved at all three levels of processing. Desmet (2010) distinguishes between three appraisals that, according to him, are universal emotional forces that hide behind all human emotions: (1) a pleasantness appraisal (the extent to which an object provides me pleasantness or pain), (2) a usefulness appraisal (the extent to which a product supports me in reaching my goals), (3) a rightfulness appraisal (the extent to which an object meets or exceeds my standards or expectations). According to Desmet (2010), appealing products correspond to those three basic human forces. In the present study, we will only focus on aesthetic emotions, which we define as pleasantness appraisal on the visceral level.

Kahneman (2011) distinguishes between two systems of processing information: one fast system (i.e. System 1 or the experience self) and one slow system (i.e. System 2 or the remembering/reflecting self). The fast system is impulsive and intuitive; the slow system is reasoning and reflective. The fast system is involved in immediate reactions, based on associations and recognitions. The slow system is involved in processes that demand more cognitive resources, such as monitoring the appropriateness of a behavior in a social situation or comparing two objects for overall value. The fast system

is the one that answers the question: “Does it hurt now?” The slow system is the one that answers the question: “How was it, on the whole? The present study will only focus on the fast system, the experience self. This system is involved in immediate emotional reactions to visual stimuli.

Basic emotions

Norman’s (2004) three levels of processing information, discussed above, reflect the evolution of the brain, starting with primitive one-celled organisms, primarily driven by the visceral level and slowly evolving to more complex animals, to vertebrates, mammals and finally, apes and humans. During evolution, basic emotions have played an important role in determining which species survive (Darwin, 1872; Ekman & Friesen, 2003). According to Ekman and Friesen (2003), the six basic emotions are: anger, fear, disgust, sadness, surprise and happiness. Basic emotions are universally recognized and universally expressed through facial expressions. When people from different cultures viewed photographs showing facial expressions of basic emotions, they had little difficulty identifying the emotion that each expression conveyed (Ekman, 1982). Such emotions are pure and not amenable to deconstructions. Basic emotions are relevant for this study, because they appear on the visceral level (Norman, 2004) and belong to such automatic activities that are attributed to the “thinking fast” system (Kahneman, 2011). Such emotions help us make quick decisions about what is good or bad, safe or dangerous, and send appropriate signals to other parts of our brain and body. This is the start of affective processing (Norman, 2004).

Personality

Despite the evidence that basic emotions seem to be universal (Ekman & Friesen, 2003), people may differ in their emotional reactions toward a specific object. Losing a loved one might be expressed in a number of ways: by openly crying and wailing (e.g. sadness), by anger and irritation (e.g. anger), by singing and dancing (e.g. happiness) or by silence and isolation (e.g. absence of emotion) (Atkinson et al., 2000). We have good reason to believe that emotional reactions of basic emotions also differ when responding to stimuli that in general might elicit less dramatic reactions, such as health-care products. Previous research (i.e. Desmet, 2008; Hong & Lee, 2010; Lau-Gesk & Myers-Levy, 2009) has shown that the appraisal process is related to several psychological factors, such as personal goals, moods, imagination, empathy, cognitive capacity and motivation. All such factors are highly subjective and might therefore differ between individuals.

Distinctions among individuals receive considerable support from an increasingly extensive amount of psychological literature on personality (Larsen & Buss, 2005). Personality is an individual’s particular combination of feelings (i.e. emotions), thoughts (i.e. cognitions) and behavior (Larsen & Buss, 2005; Lewis, 2001). The framework that has received the most attention and support from personality researchers

is the five-factor model, which was originally coined by Fiske (1949). During the 50s, 60s and 70s, several independent research teams took slightly different routes, yet all arrived at the same conclusions – most human personality traits can be boiled down into five broad dimensions of personality traits, regardless of language and culture (Larsen & Buss, 2005). The five-factor model has been empirically tested in every decade since 1949, suggesting that the structure is also replicable over time. In scientific spheres, the five-factor model is nowadays the most widely accepted and used model of personality (Holmberg & Weibull, 2010). According to Larsen and Buss (2005), key markers of the five-factor model are as follows:

- Openness (versus reticence). Open people are open to innovation, different cultures, new information and the emotions of other people. Reticent people are more conservative and reserved to innovations, cultures, information and social emotions.
- Conscientiousness (versus spontaneity). Conscientious people are forward thinking and plan their lives. Spontaneous people are more impulsive and act on the spur of the moment.
- Extraversion (versus introversion). Extravert people have a great impact on their social environment and tend to be happy. Introvert people are more quiet and tend to be more like wallflowers.
- Agreeableness (versus antagonistic). Agreeable people negotiate to resolve conflicts and strive for agreement. Antagonistic people are aggressive, assert their power to resolve social conflicts and seem to get themselves into a lot of social conflicts.
- Neuroticism (versus emotional stability). Neurotic people have a variability of moods over time, are anxious, stressed and disconnected from life and other people. Emotionally stable people are more composed, relaxed and tend to be like boats that remain on course through choppy waters.

Theorizing

In this study, we view the appraisal process for emotional reactions as a fast and immediate reactions rather than a slow process of cognitive elaborations. According to Lau-Gesk and Meyers-Levy (2009), such a perspective is more appropriate for emotions that demand less cognitive resources (e.g. basic, univalent and non-self-conscious emotions) than for emotions that demand more cognitive resources (e.g. complex, mixed and self-conscious emotions). When individuals do not have the ability (or motivation) to engage in the appraisal process, they can be said to have a neutral appraisal (Ruckler et al., in press). In our basic model, we use photos of health-care products as stimuli, personality traits as independent variables, and basic emotions and neutral as dependent variables (Figure 1). As set out in the methodology, we will control the stimuli in order to investigate the effect of personality traits on emotions.

Figure 1. Model of product emotion (Inspired by Desmet & Hekkert, 2001).

METHOD

Experimental design

This study was based on an experiment conducted with student samples. The controlled stimuli in this experiment were 13 photos of health-care products designed by the Swedish design agency Veryday. All products were designed for multinational companies (e.g. AstraZeneca, Irras, Maquet, Pfizer and Roche) and are experienced by patients around the world on a daily basis (Appendix). The specific products were selected together with designers at Veryday to represent the huge variety of emotional design in the life-science business. The inclusion criteria of products were the following: (i) The products should be intended for all adults (not especially designed for specific genders or ages), (ii) the product should still exist in hospital contexts and be the latest version, (iii) the product should be used when interacting with patients who are conscious (not under anesthesia).

Participants

Sixty-six undergraduate students participated in the study. In order to capture heterogeneous personalities, data were collected from two different student samples. The first sample consisted of 3rd year marketing students at the School of Business, Economics and Law at the University of Gothenburg (n=39). Data from this sample were collected on the 20th of January 2014. The second sample consisted of 1st and 2nd year design students at the University College of Art, Crafts and Design in Stockholm (n=27) and data from this sample were collected on the 23rd of January 2014. Fifty-two per-

cent of the participants were women (n=34) and forty-eight percent were men (n=32). The mean age was twenty-five years (M=24.8). The average number of days that the participants spent in hospital during their lifetimes was six (M=6.1). All participants were able to communicate in Swedish and 94 percent (n=62) were Swedish citizens.

Procedure

The study consisted of two parts: Firstly, participants filled in their background information and completed a personality test individually (approximately 10 minutes). Secondly, participants observed 13 photos of health-care products together on a large screen (Figure 2) and reported their emotions individually (approximately 10 minutes). For each photo, participants were told to report the emotion that best corresponded to their feeling. Participants were told to report the emotion as they experienced it and to use their gut-feeling. They were also told to report their emotions even if they could not identify the object or its usability. After each photo, a white screen was shown for 10 seconds, in order to neutralize the spill-over between photos. As will be discussed below, the emotions were reported through a combined verbal and visual self-report scale. The respondents were told to primarily focus on the visual self-report measure.

Instrument

The questionnaire covered areas such as background data (e.g. age, gender, citizenship, number of days in hospital), personality traits and emotional reactions to each product respec-

Figure 2. Participants at University College of Arts, Crafts and Design.

tively. The personality traits were measured through the HP5 inventory, a short version of the five-factor model especially adjusted for well-being and health-care studies (Gustavsson, Jönsson, Linder & Weinryb, 2003). Table 1 illustrates the link between personality traits and the specific items in HP5i. The scale used for each item was a four-level scale; completely agree (coded as 1), partly agree (coded as 2), partly disagree (coded as 3), completely disagree (coded as 4).

The emotional reaction to each photo was measured through a combined verbal and visual self-report measure. The visual self-report measure is based on photographs of universal facial expressions of basic emotions (Ekman & Friesen, 2003)

PERSONALITY TRAIT	ITEMS IN HP5
Openness (reverse scale)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I think emotions many times are exaggerated • I often have difficulties to understand other's feelings • Normally, I avoid getting involved in others problem • I do not analyze my feelings
Conscientiousness (reverse scale)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I usually act on the spur of the moment • I often throw myself too hastily into things • I usually talk before I think • I am an impulsive person
Extraversion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I often feel exhilarated • I usually enjoy life • I am usually in a good mood when I socialize • I am keen on trying out new things
Agreeableness (reverse scale)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I often make sarcastic commentaries • I usually behave vengefully if I am treated badly • I usually come up with piercing and malicious answers • Someone who offends me, can count on trouble
Neuroticism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I often feel uncomfortable and ill at ease • I often feel pressure when I have to speed up • I often have muscles so tense that I get tired • Unexpected noise makes me jump

Table 1. Link between personality traits and items
Source: Gustavsson et al, 2003

Figure 3. Verbal and visual emotions used in the self-report measure.

	Sadness	Anger	Fear	Disgust	Positive surprise	Happiness	Neutral	Pleasant affect	Unpleasant affect
Openness (r)	0.02	0.09	0.25	-0.19	0.25	-0.79*	-0.06	-0.16	0.16
Conscientiousness (r)	0.01	0.50	0.14	0.24	0.63**	-0.19	-0.41**	0.33*	0.19
Extraversion	-0.93*	0.19	0.80**	0.27	0.58	0.35	-0.62**	0.58*	0.29
Agreeableness (r)	-0.15	0.00	-0.24	0.26	-0.22	0.00	0.18	-0.09	-0.14
Neuroticism	-0.37	0.36	0.38*	0.38	0.00	0.19	-0.34*	0.10	0.29*
Intercept	1.22	-6.82*	-5.48**	-5.14**	-5.53**	-2.28	3.46**	-3.91**	-2.79**
Nagelkerke R ²	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.01

Table 2. The relationship between personality traits and emotional reactions. (Binominal logistic regression. Log odds)
 Note. $p < 0.01$: **; $p < 0.05$: *. $r =$ reversal. $n = 766$. Pleasant affect = positive surprise + happiness. Unpleasant affect = sadness + anger + fear + disgust.

and constructed together with designers at Veryday in Sweden (Figure 3).

Data analysis

Several logistic regression analyses were performed with a certain basic emotion, neutral or affect as dependent variables and the five personality traits as independent variables. The affect variables were constructed through the basic emotions, which means that the sum of positive surprise and happiness were used to construct a pleasant affect and that the sum of sadness, fear, disgust and anger were used to construct an unpleasant affect. A total of 766 pictures were analyzed in each logistic regression, based on reactions from 66 persons.

Findings

The key-findings are (1) a high degree of extraversion influences the experience of a more pleasant affect; (2) a high degree of neuroticism influences the experience of a more unpleasant affect, especially fear; (3) a low degree of conscientiousness influences the experience of a pleasant affect in terms of positive surprise; (4) a high degree of openness

influences the experience of happiness; (5) a high degree of extraversion influences the experience of fear, while a low degree of extraversion influences the experience of sadness; (6) a low degree of extraversion, a low degree of neuroticism and/or a low degree of conscientiousness influence the absence of emotional experience, neutral (Table 2).

DISCUSSION

Methodological considerations

The present study has a number of methodological limitations that might be related to each other. Firstly, the study was conducted in an unnatural context: a classroom where students were told to emotionally respond to photos of health-care products. Real life experiences most often involve multiple and interrelated emotions that evolve and interact with each other, with the event at hand, and with our reactions to these events (Fokkinga & Desmet, 2012). Secondly, the study only focused on basic and univalenced emotions (compared to complex and mixed emotions). In the present study, our focus was on aesthetic emotions with appraisals in terms of intrinsic pleasantness, rather than more complex emotions (e.g. instrumental and social emotions) with usefulness and

rightfulness appraisals (Desmet, 2003; 2010). However, there are most likely more emotions that could have been characterized as aesthetic emotions than the six basic emotions of Ekman (1982) used here. With the use of PrEmo for instance, participants are able to express blends of 14 distinct emotional reactions through a non-verbal measure (Desmet, Overbeeke & Tax, 2001). Thirdly, the study only focused on measuring emotions in the moment (compared to reflections and memories). This implies that our findings relate to the experience self rather than the remembering self (Kahneman, 2011), and should be applied to appearance in visceral design rather than self-conscious emotions (e.g. proud, guilt) in reflective design (Norman, 2004; Lau-Gesk & Meyers-Levy, 2009).

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

Personality traits, positive emotions and pleasant affect

We found that three traits are associated with positive emotions and/or pleasant affect: (1) a high degree of extraversion, (2) a high degree of openness and (3) a low degree of conscientiousness (i.e. more impulsive). Our first finding corresponds to previous research, which has found that a high degree of extraversion is associated to subjective well-being and pleasant affect (Diener & Lucas, 1999; Larsen & Buss, 2005). Our second finding also corresponds to previous research. A higher degree of openness is often slightly positively correlated with a pleasant affect (i.e. happiness), although the relationship between openness and a pleasant affect is much weaker than the relationship between extraversion and a pleasant affect (Diener & Lucas, 1999; Larsen & Buss, 2005). In the present study, we have found that openness influences happiness rather than positive surprise. It might be that individuals with a high degree of openness are more open to sudden impulses, which makes them less surprised. Our third finding is more unexpected. To the best of our knowledge, the relationship between positive surprise and impulsivity, in the moment, has not previously been explored. What we know from advertising research is that individuals in need of a high degree of control are difficult to persuade through simple emotional appeals, compared to individuals that require a lower degree of control (Morales, Wu & Fitzsimons, 2012). This might support our finding that impulsive individuals respond more emotionally than other individuals, but not particularly why they respond with a pleasant affect. Ramathan and Williams (2007) have found that prudent individuals (i.e. conscientious) focus more on problems while impulsive individuals focus more on hedonic pleasure. The combination of these two studies (Morales, Wu & Fitzsimons, 2012; Ramathan & Williams, 2007) gives some support to our finding: that impulsive people respond more frequently with pleasant affect compared to people in general. However, we have not found any support from previous research for why individuals respond with positive surprise rather than happiness. It might be because surprise refers to a sudden and unexpected

increase of arousal (Apter, 2007). According to Desmet (2008), positive surprise (i.e. astonishment) has a higher arousal than happiness (i.e. joyfulness). Impulsivity has been associated with thrill and novelty seeking; for instance, in experimenting with drugs (Castellanos-Ryan & Conrod, 2012) and in compulsive buying (Sun, Wu & Youn, 2004). The higher level of arousal might therefore explain why positive surprise, rather than happiness, is related to lack of impulse control. The pleasant affect might appear in the moment, as we measure here, but does not need to cause more pleasant affect in total, when long-term effects are included.

Personality traits, negative emotions and unpleasant affect

We have found that negative emotions and/or unpleasant affect are related to neuroticism and extraversion. The first finding, the relation between a high degree of neuroticism and a negative reaction to visual stimuli is well known and well documented (Diener & Lucas, 1999; Larsen & Buss, 2005; Canli et al., 2001; Fox, Ridgewell & Ashwin, 2009). Fox (2012), explains the relationship between neuroticism and fear through neurobiological mechanisms, so-called serotonin transporter genes; “People with a short form of serotonin transporter gene have an emergency brain that reacts much more vigorously to danger” (Fox, 2012, p. 111). The second finding is more interesting and might be provocative for some personality theorists. This finding questions one of the most fundamental principles in the five-factor model of personality: that extraversion relates to the pleasant affect, but not to the unpleasant affect (Costa & McCrae, 1980). If we limit our scope to only measuring the unpleasant affect, our finding corresponds to previous research (Table 2). However, several researchers (i.e. Desmet, 2008; Russel, 1980) argue that the unpleasant affect is too broad a concept and thus propose more distinct emotions, based on an individual’s level of arousal. Fear, for instance, has a much higher arousal than sadness. The present study shows that extraversion is related to distinct emotions of the unpleasant affect; a high degree of extraversion influences fear, while a low degree of introversion influences sadness. This finding has high construct validity because it is in line with the theoretical ideas behind the trait under consideration: extraversion. Extroverts are more vigorous and active than introverts and therefore experience the unpleasant affect with a high degree of arousal (i.e. fear), while introverts are more quiet and calm than extroverts and therefore experience the unpleasant affect with a low degree of arousal (i.e. sadness).

Personality traits and the absence of emotions and affects

We found that a low degree of neuroticism, a low degree of extraversion and a high degree of conscientiousness influence the absence of emotional reaction (i.e. neutral). In contrast to many previous studies (i.e. Costa & McCrae, 1980; Canli et al., 2001) on positive and negative reactions to stimuli, this study allowed a “neutral” response alternative. However, our

findings are not very spectacular. According to previous research, a high degree of extraversion and a high degree of neuroticism are the personality traits that have been most closely related to emotion and affect (Diener & Lucas, 1999). If those traits are low (as for introverts and/or emotionally stable people), the probability for a neutral response should increase, which corresponds to our findings (Table 2). The relationship between a high degree of conscientiousness and a neutral response is less explored. This finding corresponds to our previous discussion regarding conscientious people; individuals that desire self-control are more difficult to persuade through simple emotional appeals (Morales, Wu & Fritzmons, 2012). To the best of our knowledge, no previous study has found that individuals with a low degree of neuroticism, a low degree of extraversion and/or a high degree of conscientiousness are particularly emotional in their reactions to stimuli in psychometric self-rating scales or in neurobiological measures, such as fMRI (Costa & McCrae, 1980; Canli et al., 2001; Fox, Ridgewell & Ashwin, 2009). With regards to the theoretical ideas behind openness, as well as the measurement items, we found it surprising that people with a low degree of openness did not respond more neutrally. One explanation might be that the health-care products used in this study are not very emotional. According to Moore, Harris and Chen (1995), people with a high degree of affect intensity respond more strongly only when it comes to affective ads, not neutral ads. A related explanation might be that photos of health-care products in a classroom seldom evoke mixed emotions (although it is hard to know as we did not allow multiple responses). Previous research (Hong & Lee, 2010) has found that people with a high degree of openness (i.e. a high degree of abstract thinking) are literally more open for processing and responding positively to appeals with mixed emotions (Hong & Lee, 2010; Fokkinga & Desmet, 2012). An alternative explanation might be that people with a high degree of openness respond with positive emotions when they experience mixed emotions, while people with a low degree of openness do not explore mixed emotions to the same degree, and therefore more easily respond with a univalent emotion, either pleasant or unpleasant.

Implication for designers

Norman (2004) stated that personality traits are important for designers to consider because they will influence whether a person will be satisfied by a certain product or not:

“Personality theories divide people along such dimensions as extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, emotional stability, and openness. To designers, this means that no single design will satisfy everyone”. (Norman, 2004, p. 39).

It is worth noting that Norman uses the terminology “satisfy”, an instrumental emotion related to goal compliance, and a reflective and overall judgment of the design object, rather than an aesthetic emotion in the moment of experiencing. However, elsewhere Norman (2004) discusses personality traits in relation to aesthetic emotions. According to him, such emotions help people to make fast decisions regarding what is good or

bad, safe or dangerous, and send appropriate signals to other parts of our brain and body, and thereby start the whole system of affective processing. An injection *in the eye of the patient* [Appendix, Picture 7] might be a very emotional experience. If designers know that health-care products evoke more fear in some patients than others, they can make sure that they recruit appropriate candidates for the user studies. If designers are able to reduce fear appeals among patients with a high degree of neuroticism by addressing product design, they are probably also able to reduce it for all other patients, which is in line with arguments related to Design for all/Inclusive design/Universal design. Truly understanding the needs of all users, guaranteeing input from all types of individuals (even those that are not so explicit), set the foundation for a greater match between user needs and product success.

It is worth remembering that researchers first started to be interested in emotions because emotions were perceived to have survival values for species (Darwin, 1872). In certain kinds of contexts, small stimuli might have a huge impact and greater meaning. An experience of fear in a hospital might imply the end is near.

In recent years, modern health care systems have become more personalized, preventive and proactive. This is in line with the results of this study, which show that on an emotional level, users react differently to health-care stimuli depending on their personality. However, the challenge is to design a health care system that can actually respond differently to different patient personalities. The possibility to adjust health-care products to individual needs and desires might be restricted for a number of reasons (e.g. financial, market structure, competitors, business and political priorities, etc.). In practice, it is more realistic to provide individually adjusted services within the realm of digital health-care, rather than products. We suggest more research in this field, to find out how personality is related to the needs and desires in interactive and digital health care service systems.

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APPENDIX - PHOTOS OF HEALTH CARE PRODUCTS

Picture 1

Picture 2

Picture 3

Picture 4

Picture 5

Picture 6

Picture 7

Picture 8

Picture 9

Picture 10

Picture 11

Picture 12

Picture 13

AESTHETIC BALANCE IN THREE DIFFERENT EMOTIONS

Carlos Cordoba-Cely

Department of Design, University of Nariño, Av. Torobajo 47-150, Pasto, Colombia.

✉ cordobacely@udenar.edu.co

ABSTRACT

Aesthetic balance is an active process of perception to identify i) the regularity and ii) the novelty of a stimulus. This article finds the aesthetic balance of a prototypical web page and establishes the influence of the regularity and the novelty of the product on three affective experiences: beauty, satisfaction and enjoyment. The results show that aesthetic balance equally affects the beauty, while the dimension of regularity leads to satisfaction, and the dimension of novelty leads to enjoyment. The implications of these results are discussed.

KEYWORDS: *Aesthetic Balance, Aesthetic Experience, Design Theory.*

INTRODUCTION

A user's interpretation of a product is a multifaceted experience that can address aesthetic experiences as well as meaningful and affective ones (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007). Thus, while an aesthetic experience seeks the delight of the product through different sensory modalities and focuses on the perception of the object, a meaningful experience seeks partnering with various abstract qualities and focuses on the cognition of the product. Finally, affective experience refers to emotions caused by the aesthetic and/or meaningful dimensions of a product on the user. Despite the clear perceptual orientation of the aesthetics, it is known that there are two components that identify i) the regularity and ii) the novelty of the stimulus (Gombrich, 1984). Variations of this double condition determines what is known as aesthetic balance (Coates, 2003), which has been studied under different names in Marketing (Creusen & Snelders, 2002; Creusen & Schoormans, 2005), Architecture (Nasar, 1984, 1999), Design (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007; Coates, 2003; Locher, Overbeeke & Wensveen, 2010), Semantic Theory (Krippendorff & Butter, 1984; Steffen, 2007, 2009) Visual Arts (Arnheim, 1966; Gombrich, 1984; Hekkert, 2006), Psychology (Russell, 2003; Norman, 2004a; Locher *et al.*, 2007) and Human-Computer Interaction (Tractinsky, Katz & Ikar, 2000; Hassenzahl, 2003; Lindgaard *et al.*, 2006) among others. Given this approach, this article seeks to find the influence of the aesthetic balance of a prototypical web page on three different emotions accord-

ing to Desmet's classification of product emotions (2003): Beauty (aesthetic emotion), Satisfaction (instrumental emotion) and Enjoyment (interest emotion). For this purpose, this article presents a theoretical foundation about aesthetic balance as a two dimensional theoretical construct that captures the regularity -Classical Aesthetics- and novelty -Expressive Aesthetic- of a product (Gombrich, 1984, Lavie & Tractinsky, 2004). To test the Balance Aesthetic, first a group of experts analyzed the learning platform of the University of Nariño looking at prototypical forms of regularity and novelty following Reber, Shwarz & Winkielman (2004). Second, the validity and reliability of the scales used to measure the classical and expressive dimensions were determined. Subsequently, each of these dimensions was correlated with beauty to compare individual variance that was explained using a nested model procedure (Edwards, 2001; Burton-Jones & Straub, 2006). Following Coates (2003) and Tractinsky *et al.* (2006), equilibrium between these two dimensions and beauty is expected. Finally, the impact of excluding each of the dimensions in the explained variance of beauty, satisfaction and enjoyment has been determined. With this procedure, we expected to find the different impacts of aesthetic balance on the chosen emotions. Thus, a greater impact on the exclusion of classical aesthetics on satisfaction (Lindgaard & Dudek, 2003), as well as a greater impact on the exclusion of expressive aesthetics on the enjoyment (Sanchez-Franco & Roldan, 2005) is expected.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

As part of the aesthetic experience, beauty is an active process of perception between the formal characteristics of the stimulus and the sensory modalities of the person that seeks to find the balance between i) regularity and ii) novelty underlying an object (Arnheim, 1966, Gombrich, 1984; Coates, 2003). The interaction of these attributes provides different affective responses to the product that can range from visceral emotions to deeper affective evaluations (Desmet, 2003; Hekkert, 2006; Desmet & Hekkert, 2007; Norman 2004a, 2004b). This double condition is a part of the discussion between Objective Aesthetic and Subjective Aesthetics. That is, whether beauty is a property of the object or a person's judgment. The importance of this issue lies in the fact that the appeal could be addressed as a perceptual stimulus (e.g. Gestalt psychology), or as a subjective judgment (e.g. product Semiotics). If it is done using the first approach, the aesthetic experience is reduced to an innate mechanism that recognizes simple patterns of survival and formal identification (e.g. Karvonen, 2000, Norman, 1988). In contrast, if undertaken using the second approach, it is assumed that an aesthetic experience is first of all meaningful, where the cognitive exercise and symbolic judgments of the observer come first (e.g. Pickford, 1972; Hassenzahl, 2003; Hassenzahl, 2004b). As pointed out by Lavie & Tractinsky (2004), current theories have assumed an intermediate position in which beauty is approached from the characteristics of the stimulus and the individual's expectations. Meanwhile, Gombrich (1984) believes that the importance of this discussion focuses on an intermediate point where the underlying regularity of the stimulus is investigated, as well as the discovery of deviations that raise our affect for novelty.

It is important to note that in this study, the author assumes that judgments of aesthetic experiences are different from the judgments of meaningful experiences (Crilly, Moultrie & Clarkson, 2004; Desmet & Hekkert, 2007), because the former are related to the formal components of a product, whereas the latter are related to its functional interpretations and symbolic associations (Hassenzahl, 2008). From this perspective, it is necessary to distinguish between the three levels of mental processing to measure the aesthetic: Visceral, Cognitive and Reflective (Norman, 2004a). When approached as a set of attributes that evaluate the formal characteristics of the product, it is considered a measure of visceral aesthetic (e.g. Lavie & Tractinsky, 2004); however, if approached as a set of attributes that evaluate the functional and symbolic associations (e.g. Hassenzahl, 2003) it is considered a measure with cognitive or reflective emphasis (Tractinsky, 2004). Following Norman (2004b), the approach taken in this paper holds that the aesthetic balance is associated with the visceral level of processing. However, the beauty, satisfaction and enjoyment as general and abstract emotional responses are associated with the level of reflective processing (Hassenzahl, 2004b; Desmet & Hekkert, 2007) as shown in Figure 1.

Aesthetic Balance

The measurement of beauty from aesthetic balance has been used by various authors such as Nasar (1984; 1999) with the attributes of order and diversity in the city, Steffen (2007; 2009) with the concepts of order and complexity in product language of clothing, Coates (2003) with the factors of information and concinnity, and Lavie & Tractinsky (2004) with the dimensions of classical and expressive aesthetics, among others. In all the previous examples, it is implicitly assumed that beauty is a higher order theoretical construction consisting of this double condition. It is evident that any variation in this duality will involve changes in perception and judgment of the product. This is illustrated by Arnheim (1966) when he claims that the complexity without order produces confusion and order without complexity produces boredom. Similarly, Gombrich (1984) states that aesthetic pleasure lays somewhere between boredom and confusion and Reber et al. (2004) agree when talking about perceptual fluency. Coates (2003) is more specific and assumes that the aesthetic ingredients of a product resemble a balance between factors of Information and Concinnity. The information factor is based on Shannon & Weaver (1949)'s model of information codification between the object and the person as a communication system. Thus, the difference of contrast and novelty between the mental model and the *expected object* is measured in the product. The increase of contrast and novelty, expands the information that is reflected as increased cognitive arousal. On the other hand, the concinnity factor measures the normality of the product attributes and the similarity between the mental model and the *hoped object*. The increase of concinnity increases compatibility, which is reflected in less information and cognitive interest. Only if there is a balance between novelty and concinnity is there an adequate amount of information and therefore a positive visual attractiveness is obtained (i.e. positive valence). In contrast, if there is only cognitive arousal, the appeal will be confusing and if concinnity also exists, the appeal will be neutral or boring. It can be said then that the aesthetic balance consists in the variations between dimensions that measure the perception of regularity and the novelty of the product. Following Lavie and Tractinsky (2004), it is believed that this approach to measuring this double condition improves users' analysis and understanding to judge the beauty and other emotions of a stimulus. Thus, it is suggested that satisfaction is an affective reaction given by the stimulus of perceived regularity while enjoyment is an affective reaction given by the stimulus of perceived novelty. In the case of beauty, the affective reaction is a value judgment resulting from the balance between regularity and novelty.

METHOD

Considering the theoretical background, it can be said that the structure of aesthetic balance is modeled as an aggregate construct with two composite dimensions that jointly capture the regularity and novelty of the product. The scale to measure each of these dimensions is based on Lavie & Tractinsky

(2004)'s Classical and Expressive Aesthetics. This scale was chosen for several reasons: (1) it is a scale designed to measure the user's experience beyond the experts' experience. This is important because the validation was carried out with a group of engineering students who did not have a comprehensive knowledge of the aesthetic issue. (2) It is a scale comprised of two dimensions: one designed to measure the regularity of the product and the other, designed to measure the novelty of the product. This scale also shows good reliability of data obtained through a process of four studies. (3) It is a scale that has been replicated in other studies, especially in the measurement of different websites (see Sutcliffe & De Angeli, 2005; De Angeli, Sutcliffe & Hartmann, 2006; Hartmann, Sutcliffe, & De Angeli, 2008).

Thus, from the original scale, the following terms of the classical dimension were extracted: Symmetric, Clear, and Pleasant. The following terms of the expressive dimension were also extracted: Original, Sophisticated, and Fascinating. Finally, the terms Ordered and Complexity were added (Arnheim, 1966; Steffen, 2007, 2009) for each of the dimensions proposed.

Design

Prior to the study, a group of experts in web design - consisting of five doctoral students in Multimedia Engineering from the Polytechnic University of Catalonia - found in the virtual campus of University of Nariño (<http://uvirtual.udenar.edu.co/>) easily identifiable prototypical forms of symmetry, figure-ground contrast, visual clarity and information (Reber et al., 2004). Figure 2 shows the screenshot of the platform

CONSTRUCT	ITEMS
Classic Aesthetic	CA1. The virtual campus is ordered
	CA2. The virtual campus is symmetric
	CA3. The virtual campus is clear
	CA4. The virtual campus is pleasant
Expressive Aesthetic	EA5. The virtual campus is complexity
	EA6. The virtual campus is original
	EA7. The virtual campus is sophisticated
	EA8. The virtual campus is fascinating
Beauty	B9. The virtual campus is beauty
Satisfaction	S10. The interaction with the virtual campus has been satisfactory
	S11. The interaction with the virtual campus has been a positive experience
Enjoyment	E12. I enjoyed using the virtual campus
	E13. The interaction with the virtual campus has been a pleasant experience
	E14. Experience with the virtual campus has been enjoyable

Table 1: Measurement Scales

where it is possible to see the web page fulfilling the criterion of prototypical stimulus. To Reber et al. (2004) all prototypical stimuli allow better perceptual fluency and greater aesthetic experience.

The study involved one hundred and thirty-three engineering students from the University of Nariño (44 female and 89 male whose age average was 19), in an online survey based on their impressions of the virtual campus of the university. Students assessed the new website design using a 5-point scale ranging from (1) "Strongly disagree" to (5) "Strongly agree". In addition to assessing product regularity and novelty, students were asked to rate the Beauty of the website (aesthetic emotion), Satisfaction (instrumental emotion) and Enjoyment (interest emotion) obtained when using this educational platform following Desmet's (2003) classification of product emotions. Thus, beauty is seen as a more general and abstract emotional response (Hassenzahl, 2004b) resulting from the aesthetic balance of the product. The items regarding Satisfaction were taken from Hong, Thong & Tam (2006), and the ones concerning Enjoyment were taken from Sanchez-Franco & Roldan (2005). The final questionnaire contained 14 items, as shown in Table 1.

RESULTS

Table 2 shows the results obtained with the factorial loadings and the reliability of the scale. The Composite Reliability (CR) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) were obtained using the PLS-Graph software, and the factor loadings and Cronbach's alpha using SPSS software. The term Pleasant (CA4) was excluded because it was loaded on Expressive Aesthetics (0.502) and the term Complexity was excluded (EA5) to improve the Cronbach's alpha coefficient (0.550 if item is not deleted) on the Expressive Aesthetics. Following Nunnally (1978), a value of 0.7 will be a reliable "modest" in early stages of research and a stricter value 0.8 will be more appropriate for basic research. Thus, the two dimensions showed adequate reliability to overcome the suggested minimum value.

In terms of validation, Table 3 shows the discriminant validity of the dimensions by means of the square root of AVE that should be above 0.50 in the diagonal of the table, thus, establishing that over 50% of the variance of construct is due to its indicators (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Besides beauty, the results obtained with satisfaction and enjoyment were included for later discussion.

Testing Nested Models

Following Edwards (2001) and Burton-Jones & Straub (2006), each of the aesthetic dimensions was first tested separately by examining the values of the variance explained (R^2) on beauty with the software PLS-Graph and using bootstrapping technique with 500 re-sampling and centroid. Next, the two dimensions were tested together but as separate components, and finally the two composite dimensions were tested as an aggregate construct called Aesthetic Balance. As expected, it

was found that there is a higher amount of R² when aesthetic balance is used as an aggregate theoretical construct, namely as a theoretical definition resulting from the combination of its dimensions. Table 4 shows the results obtained.

The higher-order model was constructed using factor scores for each sub-construct.

As models of Table 4 are nested, it is possible to compare the degree to which each of the dimensions of aesthetic balance explains the beauty of the website as well as the satisfaction and enjoyment. To measure the relative impact of the dimensions on these three constructs, the change in the value of R² when any one of the dimensions is removed was compared. The effect size (f^2) was calculated by the formula $(R^2_{full} - R^2_{excluded}) \div (1 - R^2_{full})$ (Mathieson, et al, 2001). For his part,

Cohen (1988) suggests an f^2 of 0.02 as small, 0.15 as medium and 0.35 as large (see Chin, 1998). Multiplying f^2 by $(n - k - 1)$ where n is the sample size and k is the number of independent variables, it is possible to obtain a pseudo F test to the statistical significance of f^2 (Mathieson et. al 2001). Table 5 shows the results obtained. As expected, the greater impact to exclude the regularity—classical aesthetic—was on the satisfaction, whereas the greater impact to exclude novelty—expressive aesthetic—was on the enjoyment.

Figure 3 shows the f^2 for the three measured emotions. As expected, the change in aesthetic balance is more balanced in terms of beauty than in the other emotions. Below, the implications of the results are discussed.

DISCUSSION

The aesthetic balance is primarily associated with the visceral level of processing a stimulus as shown by other studies (Berlyne, 1971; Tractinsky, et al 2006; Lindgaard et al, 2006). However, the affective reaction based on the fluency variations of aesthetic balance produce (Reber et al., 2006), influences the emotional responses associated with the level of reflective processing. The findings in this study show that the aesthetic balance can be a good predictor of three different emotions: Beauty (aesthetic emotion) Satisfaction (instrumental emotion) and Enjoyment (interest emotion). Each relationship is discussed next.

ITEM	CLASSIC AESTHETIC	EXPRESSIVE AESTHETIC	COMPOSITE RELIABILITY
CA1	0.647***	0.292	0.845
CA2	0.631***	0.208	
CA3	0.750***	0.150	
EA6	0.353	0.576***	0.784
EA7	0.179	0.760***	
EA8	0.199	0.570***	

*** All item-to-construct loadings are significant ($p < 0.001$).

Table 2: Measurement Scales for aesthetic dimensions

	CLASSIC AESTHETIC	EXPRESSIVE AESTHETIC	SATISFACTION	ENJOYMENT	BEAUTY
Classic Aesthetic	0.803*				
Expressive Aesthetic	0.501	0.741*			
Satisfaction	0.601	0.470	0.901*		
Enjoyment	0.530	0.474	0.574	0.878*	
Beauty	0.437	0.459	0.524	0.486	1.000

*The values in bold on the diagonal are the square root of each construct's AVE. Off-diagonal elements are correlations between constructs.

Table 3: Discriminant validity for aesthetic dimensions

MODEL	PATH COEFFICIENTS /WEIGHT	T-STATISTICS	R ²
[AB_1]	BCA= 0.452	TCA= 4.801***	R ² =0.204
	BEA= 0.471	TEA= 7.322***	R ² =0.222
[AB_2]	BCA= 0.291	TCA= 2.319*	R ² =0.286
	BEA= 0.328	TEA= 2.954**	
[AB_3]	WCA= 0.257	TAB= 10.028***	R ² =0.314
	BAB= 0.560		
	WEA= 0.242		

CA= Classical Aesthetic; EA= Expressive Aesthetic; AB= Aesthetic Balance; B: the path coefficient between an antecedent and beauty.; W= The weight of the subconstruct on the higher order usage construct in PLS. t-value significant at * $p < 0.5$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Table 4: Structural Models Tested

EMOTIONS	R ² FULL	CLASSIC AESTHETIC			EXPRESSIVE AESTHETIC		
		R ² EXCLUDED	f ²	EFFECT SIZE	R ² EXCLUDED	f ²	EFFECT SIZE
Beauty	0.31	0.22	0.13*	small	0.20	0.16*	medium
Satisfaction	0.44	0.22	0.39*	large	0.36	0.13*	small
Enjoyment	0.39	0.24	0.24*	large	0.28	0.18*	medium

*significant at pseudo F test (see Mathieson, et al, 2001).

Table 5: Exclusion Impact of Dimensions of Aesthetic Balance

Aesthetic Balance and Beauty

Following the relations of Figure 1, beauty is understood as a high-level evaluative construct measured by the balance between the perception of regularity—classical aesthetics—and perception of novelty—aesthetic-expressive—both potential determinants of low level (Hassenzahl, 2004a) known as aesthetic balance (Coates, 2003). This double condition allows us to use the aesthetic balance as an aggregate construct, which is only a composite of its dimensions that when combined produce a better explained variance of the studied theoretical issue (Law, Wong & Mobley, 1998). Among the benefits of taking the aesthetic balance as an aggregate construct are (1) it can provide holistic representations of a complex phenomenon as aesthetic experience, (2) many of the important results in research about aesthetic are factorially complex and can only be explained through predictors composite, and (3) it is possible to evaluate specific dimensions of aesthetic balance by the process of nested models (for more information about constructs see Law et al, 1998; Edwards & Bagozzi, 2000; Edwards, 2001; Petter, Straub & Rai, 2007). Thus, Table 4 allows us to conclude that the balance aesthetic as an aggregate construct better explains beauty with its combined dimensions ($R^2 = 0.314$) than with its dimensions separately ($R^2 = 0.286$). Similarly, it can be seen that in the first two models in Table 4, the influence of the expressive dimension on the variance of beauty is superior to the classical dimension - in the first model $BCA = 0.45$ vs. $BEA = 0.47$, and the second model $BCA = 0.29$ vs. $BEA = 0.32$. Given that the evaluated website is clearly task-oriented, one would expect to see greater influence of the classical dimension on the expressive dimension (see Davis, Bagozzi & Warshaw, 1992; Hassenzahl, 2003, Sanchez-Franco & Roldan, 2005; Hassenzahl & Monk, 2010). However, this only happens in the third model when the influence of the dimensions as part of an aggregate construct is studied ($WCA = 0.25$ vs. $WEA = 0.24$). This adjustment, besides the explained variance, suggests better outcomes for aesthetic balance as an aggregate construct to measure beauty.

On the other hand, the similarity of the data found between the classical dimension ($r = 0.43$, $f^2 = 0.13$) and the expressive dimension ($r = 0.45$, $f^2 = 0.16$), confirms the approach of Coates (2003) on the equilibrium of aesthetic balance and beauty as an affective experience. It is possible to say then that beauty is an evaluative judgment that measures the balance between the novelty and regularity of a product. Additionally, this equilibrium changes over time and with the target user's profile. For

example, the degree of novelty always decreases over time until the appearance of the product becomes familiar to the user. The same applies to user expectations, because the novelty depends on the comparative difference between the expected experience and the gained experience (Coates, 2003). When analyzing the results of the aesthetic balance of a product this should always be considered. In the case of the evaluated website in this study, the highest correlation and impact of the expressive dimension is explained by the recent design of the web interface and the user's profile with little experience of working in Learning Management Systems (LMS). Unlike the expressive dimension, the classical dimension is objective and therefore more predictable. Concepts such as symmetry, order and contrast never change over time and perhaps for this reason they tend to be judged with higher interpersonal homogeneity (Gombrich, 1984; Coates, 2003; Hassenzahl, 2008). Thus, the classical dimension measures the compatibility between the *hoped* regularity and the obtained regularity. For example, the website under study is task-oriented and therefore we expect a degree of regularity that does not distract or confuse users with irrelevant or noisy information.

Aesthetic Balance, Satisfaction and Enjoyment

The results in Table 3 and Table 5 show the variations of aesthetic balance and their respective influence on satisfaction and enjoyment, which are consistent with the results of other investigations. In the case of the classical dimension, it was found that their influence on the satisfaction variable has the highest correlation ($r = 0.60$) and impact ($f^2 = 0.39$). According to Lindgaard & Dudek (2003), satisfaction is a complex construct with several affective components linked to the expected use. For this reason, it is an emotion that is geared towards goal achievement (Desmet, 2003) that has been used to confirm the user's expectations (Oliver, 1993). Thus, we expected to find a higher influence of the classical dimension on satisfaction than on other affective experiences. In the case of the expressive dimension, findings showed that their influence on enjoyment has the highest correlation ($r = 0.47$) and impact ($f^2 = 0.18$). Enjoyment has been used as a construct of the user's intrinsic motivation (Davis et al, 1992), and this means that it seeks to measure the pleasure of a person to engage in any activity while browsing or trying to understand something new (Vallerand & Rattele, 2002). These types of activities that do not require apparent reinforcement (Sanchez-Franco & Roldan, 2005) but raise interest in the novelty of product are geared towards measuring the hedonic characteristics of

	SATISFACTION	BEAUTY	ENJOYMENT
Definition	Positive reflective response to the existence of more regularity in the aesthetic balance	Positive reflective response to the existence of equality between regularity and innovation in the aesthetic balance	Positive reflective response to the existence of more novelty in the aesthetic balance
Feature	Oriented to device and extrinsic motivations	Oriented aesthetic experience (user + artifact)	Oriented to user and intrinsic motivations
Example	Learning Management System (moodle)	Social Network	
(Facebook)	Microbloggings		
(Templates Tumblr)			
Graph	[Graph_Satisfaction]	[Graph_Beauty]	[Graph_Enjoyment]
CA= Classical Aesthetic; EA= Expressive Aesthetic; AB= Aesthetic Balance.			

Table 6: Aesthetic Balance and emotional dimensions

a system (Desmet, 2003; Heijden, 2004). Thus, the influence of the expressive dimension on enjoyment is consistent with the results found.

Aesthetic Balance and Design

Finally, it is important to note that this study focuses on the design as a communication process whereby the product is the linkage between the designer's intentions and the user's interpretations (Crilly, Matravers & Clarkson, 2008; Crilly, Maier & Clarkson, 2008). The results obtained here are centered on the user's interpretations and they are analyzed as an experience of access to information in relation to products based on their emotional dimensions, as proposed in Table 6.

This narrative experience of the product (Dunne & Raby, 2001; Djajadiningrat et al, 2004) can be used to measure the balance of the aesthetic appearance of the product. However, it could also serve as input for other studies to determine the degree of aesthetic innovation from the expressive dimension (Steffen, 2007) or the aesthetics of the interaction from the classical dimension and its relation to usability (Overbeeke & Wensveen, 2003).

It is important to highlight that this approach to double aesthetic conditions, does not affect the possibilities of considering beauty from only one dimension. We believe that taking a unique conceptualization about this topic is impossible; however, we also believe that there are appropriate measures and dimensions that can be used separately or together to support a study of the aesthetic experience.

LIMITATIONS

One of the major limitations in these types of studies is to measure beauty based on cultural differences (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007). We believe that this aspect is compensated with the validity, reliability and different replications of the selected scale in other studies. Although Cronbach's alpha in

the expressive dimension was poor (0.572), the result of the composite reliability (0.784) is considered as a superior measure because the loads are fixed in the unit (Barclay, Higgins & Thompson, 1995). It is emphasized that the term *pleasant* is loaded to the expressive dimension and not to the classical dimension as expected. For Coates (2003) and Russell & Carroll (1999), this term is close to the valence dimension where the classical aesthetic is measured. However, to Hassenzahl (2004a) this term has an evaluative component that could explain the load to the expressive dimension. Another possible explanation is that the Spanish adaptation to the term has changed its semantic load. However, the translation was made taking into account the adaptation of Gurbindo & Ortega (1989) on Russell's scale. The same applies to the term *complexity* that people associate with the meaning of "confusing" instead of the interrelated parts of a system (Norman, 2010). For this reason, in the evaluation of the website, these terms were not taken into account. Even so, discriminatory validity and test nested models show that the scale is valid to measure the beauty of the product.

CONCLUSIONS

The results obtained indicate that the aesthetic balance can be used as a higher order theoretical aggregate construct with two dimensions that measure the regularity—classical aesthetics—and novelty—expressive aesthetic—of the product. Similarly, the study shows that the aesthetic balance can be a good predictor of beauty and other affective experiences such as satisfaction and enjoyment. Regularity influences the affective experiences oriented to the evaluation of tasks such as satisfaction, while novelty influences the affective experiences oriented to the user's intrinsic motivation such as enjoyment. Likewise, regularity and novelty influence beauty when it is treated as an evaluative judgment. Thus, beauty seeks the balance between the novelty and the regularity that a person perceives in a product. Finally, the double fold condition of aesthetic balance allows the use of its dimensions as inputs

in various research approaches about aesthetics such as Aesthetic Innovation or Aesthetics of Interaction.

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EVALUATING PRODUCT PERCEPTION USING EYE-TRACKING AND SEMANTIC SCALES: COMPARING REAL AND VIRTUAL REPRESENTATIONS

Juan Carlos Rojas-López, Manuel Contero, Jaime Guixeres
I3BH - Instituto Labhuman. Universitat Politècnica de València, Valencia, Spain
✉ jcrojas@labhuman.com, mcontero@labhuman.com, jguixeres@labhuman.com

Mauricio Hincapié
Institución Universitaria Salazar y Herrera, Medellín, Colombia
✉ e.hincapie@iush.edu.co

ABSTRACT

The use of 3D virtual representations is a common approach in the modern process of new product development. This work presents a preliminary study with 14 participants about comparing a real and a virtual representation of a product in order to then conduct a perception evaluation analysis. The evaluation is carried out by applying a semantic scale based on four axes: novelty, resolution, style and emotion. Also eye-tracking technology is used to analyze what design features attract participants' gaze. Preliminary results show that both virtual and real objects get similar evaluation from participants using semantic scales. However, eye-tracking results indicate that there are some small differences between gaze patterns.

KEYWORDS: *eye-tracking, semantic scales, perception.*

INTRODUCTION

Currently, there is a growing interest in the connection between neuroscience and disciplines that revolve around the economy and consumption. This link began about a decade ago, when the term "neuroeconomics" was coined (Zak, 2004). The basic aim of this new field was to better understand the decision making process in an economic context, involving cognitive psychology and neuroscience. Following this new approach, other new disciplines have emerged such as "neuromarketing" or "consumer neuroscience", whereby the main goal is the transfer of insights from neurology to research in consumer behavior by applying neuroscientific methods to marketing problems (Touhami et al., 2011).

Packaging and labeling are important tools to capture consumers' attention. Now, a growing body of empirical research has started to focus on the influence of the sensory characteristics of the packaging and covers (Ares, Deliza & Giménez, 2010; Moskowitz et al., 2009). The last few years have seen an explosion of innovation in terms of evaluation, design and

shapes of products and packaging. This activity is assisted by other disciplines, which take sensorial elements to bring us information about the preferences of future consumers. In this context, neuromarketing is also related with neuroaesthetics that is aimed at revealing the processes of how we judge the aesthetics and perception of objects (Chatterjee, 2011)

In many markets, packaging gives an important added value; here, aesthetics plays an important role in product differentiation and regardless of the consumption domain, it seems to be a positive factor to trigger some specific responses in consumers such as an immediate desire to buy (Reimann et al., 2010). Based on the work of Osgood, Suci & Tannenbaum (1957), the semantic scale (SC) has become an important instrument in the aesthetic evaluation of products, packaging or labels. Nowadays, SC techniques can be complemented by eye tracking technologies to get a better understanding of the relationship between aesthetic features and product perception by the consumer. Eye movement provides an objective indicator of where a person's overt attention (and usu-

ally also their covert attention) is focused (Hoffman & Subramaniam, 1995; Spencer & Driver, 2004). This method serves to filter visual information and potentially help to organize it. As a consequence, several parameters of oculomotor behavior (e.g., saccadic eye movements) are now frequently used; in particular, the locus of an observer's visual fixations is perhaps the single most commonly used parameter when it comes to assessing where a consumer's attention might be focused. Fixations are defined as gaze patterns in which the eyes are relatively immobile, and during which the visual system is assumed to be gathering information (Pertzob et al., 2009). Eye tracking measures can provide an objective and continuous measure of the user's reactions through eye movement and gaze (Djamasbi et al., 2010).

Semantic scales and eye tracking techniques provide somewhat different information with regard to the consumer's evaluation of a product. Combining these two techniques, we can obtain complementary information about the user perception of the product.

Using virtual prototypes in the product development process is a common approach to shorten development time, increase product quality and improve flexibility and adaptation to market changes. The application of semantic scales and eye tracking techniques using virtual models must be validated to assure that the same feedback can be obtained using stimuli coming from real objects or virtual prototypes. This work is aimed at evaluating the application of both semantic scales and eye tracking for the evaluation of a virtual and real design of a bottle.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Participants and apparatus

This study was conducted with 14 Spanish voluntary participants (8 female, 6 male) with ages ranging from 22 to 53 years ($M = 40$ years: $SD = 13.65$) who did not receive any compensation for it. All participants reported normal corrected vision, and no color-blindness.

An unobtrusive eye tracker that was capable of recording the position of the eyes at a sampling rate of 300 Hz (Tobii TX300, www.tobii.com) was used to assess the participants' visual

fixations. This device has a 23" flat HD screen and a sensor bar in the lower part of it. This setup allows participants to make large head movements, and to move freely and naturally in front of the screen. Tobii Studio 3.2.1 software was used to calibrate the eye tracker, to present the stimuli, to record the data, and to extract descriptive statistics.

Stimuli

For this study, two sets of stimuli were used. The first set was made up of studio-quality images where a single bottle is presented on a white background. The second set represented the same image content and background, but using a computer render created with UNITY software instead of real object photography. All the images (648x1080 resolution) were set to equal mean luminance and size. Front and back views of the bottle were used in the study as seen in Figure 1. Additionally other bottle perspectives were prepared (0° , 15° , 35° and 60°).

A semantic scale (SC) combined with eye-tracking measure was used to compare the perception between a real bottle against a virtual one. Semantic Differential is a technique that was proposed by Osgood, Suci & Tannenbaum (1957), to measure people's reactions to stimulus words (or concepts) by means of ratings based on bipolar scales defined with contrasting adjectives at each end (e.g. "good-bad", "tall-short"). In the context of the present work the Creative Product Analysis Model (CPAM) scale (Besemer, 2010) was used with an additional semantic axis. The original axes: novelty, resolution and style are complemented by an emotional axis. The four semantic axes are described by three pairs of bipolar words (see table 1).

Figure 1. Some stimuli shown to participants.

NOVELTY (novedad)	RESOLUTION (resolución)	STYLE (estilo)	EMOTIONAL (emocional)
Antiquated - Fashion (anticuado - de moda)	Female - Male (femenino - masculino)	Stable - Unstable (estable - inestable)	Euphoria - Tranquility (euforia - tranquilidad)
Usual - Unusual (usual - inusual)	Robust - Thin (robusto - delgado)	Wrong-crafted - Well-crafted (mal hecho - bien hecho)	Sadness - Happiness (tristeza - felicidad)
Discreet - Revolutionary (discreto - revolucionario)	Tall - Short (alto - bajo)	Durable - fragile (Durable - fragil)	Empathy - indifference (empatía - indiferencia)

Table 1. Semantic Axes (in blue color the original Spanish terms presented to participants)

Procedure

Participants had to carry out two tasks that we named A and B. Task A corresponds to the real bottle and task B employs virtual bottles. The tasks were randomly presented to the participants; after finishing A or B, the participant took a break from the other activity for 10-15 minutes, before beginning the remaining task.

The study was conducted in a quiet room under standard illumination conditions. Each participant was seated between 60-70 cm from the eye-tracker system (see figure 2). After calibration the general instructions for the task were presented on the screen for 22 seconds.

Task content (presented in figure 3) is organized into four clusters. The first cluster begins with a screen with the text “5 seconds to begin”. Then, two images showing a front and a back view of the bottle are presented consecutively. Each image was shown for 3.5 seconds. Next, a semantic scale is presented on the screen with three questions (three pairs of bipolar words). Participants had 15 seconds to read and verbalize

Figure 2. Scheme of the participant in the study.

the answer to the choice number for each question (which is codified in a value from 1 to 7). Finally a one second long white screen break is presented before starting the next cluster. The other clusters used other bottle orientations. The clusters and questions are randomly selected for each subject.

Figure 3. Task description.

Figure 4. Average scores for semantic axes.

NOVELTY				Mean	Std.Dev.	RESOLUTION				Mean	Std.Dev.
Antiquated / Fashion	Real			4.929	1.774	Female/ Male	Real			3.214	1.311
	Virtual			3.786	1.968		Virtual			3.929	1.592
Usual / Unusual	Real			2.571	0.938	Robust / Thin	Real			5.500	1.286
	Virtual			4.000	1.754		Virtual			5.143	1.292
Discreet / Revolutionary	Real			3.714	1.069	Tall / Short	Real			3.429	1.604
	Virtual			4.357	1.646		Virtual			3.429	1.828
STYLE				Mean	Std.Dev.	EMOTIONAL				Mean	Std.Dev.
Stable / Unstable	Real			2.786	1.718	Euphoria / Tranquility	Real			4.714	1.684
	Virtual			3.000	1.468		Virtual			4.857	1.512
Wrong-crafted / Well-crafted	Real			5.857	1.167	Sadness / Happiness	Real			5.000	1.754
	Virtual			4.643	1.865		Virtual			4.929	1.269
Durable / fragile	Real			3.714	1.858	Empathy / indifference	Real			3.786	1.888
	Virtual			3.500	1.743		Virtual			4.214	1.672

Table 2. Mean and standard deviation for each attribute

RESULTS AND DATA ANALYSIS

Mean values for each semantic scale are plotted in figure 4, while mean values and standard deviation data are provided in Table 2. Due to a lack of normality in sample data, a Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used to compare each attribute in the four semantic axes. There was no significant difference ($\alpha = .05$) in the scores for each semantic axis comparing virtual and real representations, except for the pair “usual – unusual” in the novelty axis ($Z = -2.052, p = .040$).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

This is a preliminary study with a reduced sample size in order to obtain experience to conduct a future study with a bigger sample size. Results show that the user responses are

very similar in both virtual and real stimuli. Eye-tracking data is usually interpreted using specific graphics representation such as heat maps and gaze plots. Absolute duration heat maps are presented in figure 5. They display the accumulated fixation duration on different locations in the image that is typically related to the amount of attention paid by the observer on specific locations.

Eye tracking results show some different gaze patterns when using images from computer renderings or real photos. The main differences in figure 5 correspond to the upper label in the front view image. The virtual bottle shows a more visible text label, which is reflected in the heat map capturing more attention from the observer. In this case, the computer image perhaps excessively simplifies the representation (it does not simulate transparency perfectly) and gives more emphasis to the text label than in the real image.

Future work will try to confirm these preliminary results by including a bigger sample. Additionally, a new experiment will be designed to analyze the impact of render quality in user perception with respect to the real object using both semantic scales and eye tracking technology.

Figure 5. Heat maps of frontal and back views (first row, real on the left, render on the right). Stimuli in second row. Color scale is aqua for low fixation time and red for high fixation time.

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DESIGN AND EMOTION INTO COLLECTIVE PUBLIC USE PRODUCTS?

Gabriela Zubaran Pizzato, Dr., Lia Buarque de Macedo Guimarães, PhD
gabriela.zubaran@ufrgs.br Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul – UFRGS
✉ liabmg@gmail.com Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul – UFRGS. Brazil.

ABSTRACT

This study presents a pilot literature review, including articles published in international Design and Ergonomics journals from 2007 to 2013. Its main goal is to identify the presence of collective use products in the current scope of Design and Emotion. The classification and analysis of those articles is based on two approaches: (i) classification of the use of products regarding: collective product / individual and consumption product/ unspecified use product (ii) emotion types: positive emotions / negative / positive and negative / unspecified emotion. The results confirm the hypothesis about the significant lack of studies focusing on emotion and directed at collective public use products.

KEYWORDS: *Design and Emotion; products of collective-public use; literature review.*

INTRODUCTION

All material things evoke emotions—strong or subtle, positive or negative, conscious or unconscious—that directly affect the way people feel, think and behave (Damásio, 2000). Emotions are a necessary part of people's lives, because people don't react to the physical qualities of things, but rather what those things mean to them (Krippendorff, 2000). The feelings associated with the pleasurable use of products include safety, pride, excitement and satisfaction (Jordan, 2000), attraction, fascination and inspiration (Desmet, 2009) and people express affection for certain products to the point of "loving them" (Russian and Hekkert, 2007). Recent developments in the design discipline focus on the importance of designing for wellbeing and happiness (Desmet, 2012; Desmet and Pohlmeier, 2013; Dorrestijn and Verbeek, 2013).

In general, the authors refer to the emotion involved in using individual products, despite the fact that studies on collective use products may (and should) be enriched with answers that translate affective and therefore emotional reactions. The design of urban elements, for example, which are products of collective public use, does not differ from other design products (Creus, 1996): all kinds of products affect the emotions of their users, because there are no emotionally neutral products (Desmet and Hekkert, 2007). For example, frustrating interactions with products can reveal adverse effects, such as insecurity, fear and even anger (Norman, 2004).

Collective and public use products are aimed at meeting the, often indispensable needs (e.g. street furniture) needs of a larger number of users, compared to individual products or even private collective usage. Based on this principle, the aim of this study is to identify how the emotion associated with collective public use products is being addressed in the field of Design and Emotion. For this, the study presents a literature review including articles published in international journals from 2007 to 2013, which corresponds to about half of the life cycle of Design and Emotion. The product use approach was decisive for the motivation of this research study, based on the following questions: what kinds of products have a greater emphasis on works that are being carried out in the field of Design and Emotion? What are these products?

PRODUCTS OF USE

In areas such as management and marketing, for example, product distinction in specific categories usually has a central idea of classification, identifying public or consumer characteristics, in order to be certain of the strategies to use in market performance. In design, different industrial product categories correspond to distinct requests in the project that require one to keep in mind the following questions (Löbach, 2001, p. 41): (i) How is the product used? (ii) What is the meaning or value of the product for the user? (iii) How many different people use the product? And (iv) Is the product used collectively or privately?

The products have direct and indirect relations with users, and the intensity of these relationships (Figure 1) should be considered in the product developing process. The further a user is from owning or using a product, the greater his indifference to it (Löbach, 2001). For this reason, public-use products have a higher predisposition to predation, requiring a greater demand for maintenance that usually comes from the public coffers.

A systematic literature review was conducted in the following steps (MAGAREY, 2001): 1) problem definition, 2) search for articles, 3) selection and critical evaluation of articles, 4) data collection, 5) data analysis.

1. **Problem definition:** The definition of the problem, which constitutes the first step of the process, is the research into the relationship between collective public use products and the scope of the publications that have been conducted by the field of Design and Emotion, published in the design and ergonomics journals.
2. **Articles search:** The search period of publications comprises the last seven years (2007 to 2013), corresponding to the second half of the Design and Emotion study field. The selection of the analysis period is based on their representativeness (approximately 50 of the lifetime of the research area) and the major upgrade of articles. As a search strategy, a search for articles was undertaken using the keywords most used in the Design and Emotion literature: “design and emotion”, “emotional design”, “emotion in design” and “affective design”. The rationale for the selection of articles published in journals—rather than those published in Congress and Symposia publications in the form of books, theses and dissertations—is due to the careful evaluation that the texts are often subjected to before being accepted.
3. **Article selection and critical evaluation:** In the sequence, in the first stage, the evaluation was conducted using titles and subsequently summaries (abstract), re-

lating articles mapped with the guiding research objective. In certain situations, due to doubts about the summary, it was necessary to read certain articles in full, in order not to leave out important items for review. The articles chosen were those whose content matched the extraction criteria, and had variables associated with the relationship between emotions felt towards the products. A total of 91 articles were identified and 17 were rejected for not referring specifically to products (e.g. activities in the medical field, education, consumer shopping attitudes). Most of the articles emphasized on the relationship between emotion and brands.

4. **Data collection:** The 74 articles mapped resulting from the previous step, constitute the sample for this study and were organized in a spreadsheet, by year of publication.
5. **Data analysis:** Reading the articles gave rise to the preparation of approaches to data evaluation that were mapped and classified: (i) products categorized by use: consumption and individual use/ public or collective use/ unspecified use and others; and (ii) types of emotions covered: positive/ negative/ positive and negative/ unspecified emotions. In terms of the use approach, consumer products and individual use have been grouped and distinguished from products of collective and public use. The classification “unspecified and other” relates to studies that address products in general (not to mention the user group for which the products are intended), as well as the products that are not part of other product groups (e.g. handicrafts, private indoor environments).

RESULTS

The 74 works sampled were found in 13 international and national journals related to different areas of knowledge (Table 1).

Figure 1. Intensity of relations between user and product usage

	<i>PRODUCTS</i>		
EMOTIONS	CONSUMPTION AND INDIVIDUAL USE	COLLECTIVE	OTHER AND UNSPECIFIED
POSITIVE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hassenzahl, M. et al. (2013). Int. Journal of Design - Couvreur, L. et al. (2013). Int. Journal of Design - Helander, M. (2013). Theoretical Issues in Ergonomics Science - Mariana S.; Linden, J. (2012). Work - Gkouskos, D.; Chenb, F. (2012), Work - Golightly, et al. (2012). Theoretical Issues in Ergonomics Science - Khalid, H. et al. (2012). Theoretical Issues in Ergonomics Science - Kamp, I. (2012). Applied Ergonomics - Postma; C. et al. (2012). Design Issues - Sonderegger, A.; Sauer, J. (2010). Applied Ergonomics - Lee, S. et al. (2009). Human Factors and Ergonomics in Manufacturing - Ludden, G.; Schifferstein, H. (2009). Int. Journal of Design - Lacey, E. (2009). Int. Journal of Design - Schifferstein, H. (2008). Int. Journal of Design - Ludden, G. et al. (2008). Design Issues - Barnes, C.; Lillford, S. (2007). CoDesign - Jordan, P.; Persson, S. (2007). CoDesign - Seva, R. et al. (2007). Applied Ergonomics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Desmet, P.; Pohlmeier, A. (2013). Int. Journal of Design - Dorrestijn, S.; Verbeek, P. (2013). Int. Journal of Design - Cho, E.; Kim, Y. (2012). Int. Journal of Design - Pizzato, G. et al. (2012). Work - Correia, W. et al. (2012). Work - Volkev, L. (2008). Design Studies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sääksjarvi, M.; Hellén, K. (2013). Int. Journal of Design - Petermans, A. et al. (2013). Int. Journal of Design - Bodker, M.; Browing, D. (2013). Int. Journal of Design - Mourthé, C.; Dejean, P. (2012) Work
NEGATIVE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fokkinga, S.; Desmet, P. (2013). Int. Journal of Design - Fokkinga, S.; Desmet, P. (2012). Design Issues - Tsao, Y.; Chan, S. (2011). Applied Ergonomics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pizzato, G. et al. (2012). Work 	
POSITIVE & NEGATIVE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hwang, J. et al. (2013). Applied Ergonomics - Sonderegger, A.; Sauer, J. (2013). Applied Ergonomics - Carbon, C. et al. (2013). Int. Journal of Design - Huang, Y.; Chen, C.; Khool, L. (2012). Int. Journal of Industrial Ergonomics - Ozcan, E.; Egmond, R. (2012). Int. Journal of Design - Kujala, S.; Nurkka, P. (2012). Int. Journal of Design - Ozkaramanli, D.; Desmet, P. (2012). Int. Journal of Design - Helander, M. et al. (2012). Theoretical Issues in Ergonomics Science - Tonetto, L.; Costa, F. (2011). Strategic Design Research Journal - Fenko, A. et al. (2010). Applied Ergonomics - Wellings, T. et al. (2010). Applied Ergonomics - Karana, E.; Hekkert, P.; Kandachar, P. (2009). Material Design - Hekkert, P.; Desmet, P. (2009). Int. Journal of Design - Chitturi, R. (2009). Int. Journal of Design - Demir, E. et al. (2009). Int. Journal of Design - Jenkins, S. et al. (2009). Int. Journal of Design 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Broek, E. et al. (2009) Applied Ergonomics - Karlsson, M. (2007). CoDesign 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stones, C. (2013). Int. Journal of Design - Reddy, S. et al. (2012). Work - van der Linden, J.; Brendlerb, C. (2012) Work - Ho, A.; Siu, K. (2012). The Design Journal - Szalma, J. (2009). Theoretical Issues in Ergonomics Science - Karana, E.; Hekkert, P.; Kandachar, P. (2008). Material & Design - Pennington, N. et al. (2007). CoDesign

	PRODUCTS		
EMOTIONS	CONSUMPTION AND INDIVIDUAL USE	COLLECTIVE	OTHER AND UNSPECIFIED
POSITIVE & NEGATIVE	-Sauer, J., Sonderegger, A. (2009). Applied Ergonomics -Seva, R.; Helander, M. (2009). Int. Journal of Industrial Ergonomics -Rompay, T. et al. (2009). Int. Journal of Design -Blijlevens, J. et al (2009). Int. Journal of Design -Spence, C.; Zampini, M. (2007) CoDesign - Porter, C.; Porter, J.; Chhibber, S. (2007). Meeting Diversity in Ergonomics -Desmet, P.; Hekkert, P. (2007). Int. Journal of Design		
UNSPECIFIED	- Kim, S.; Cho, K. (2013). Int. Journal of Design - Campenhout, L. et al. (2013). Int. Journal of Design - Lockton, D. et al. (2013). Int. Journal of Design - Blijlevens, J. et al. (2013). Int. Journal of Design - Forslund, K. et al. (2013). Int. Journal of Design -Na, Y. (2009). Human Factors and Ergonomics in Manufacturing -Chamorro-Koc, M. et al. (2008). Design Studies		- Wastiels, L. et al. (2013). Int. Journal of Design -Camposa, L. et al. (2012). Work -Karana, E.; Hekkert, P.; Kandachar, P. (2010). Materials and Design

Table 1. Publications with kinds of emotions and products

Classifications of articles according to the category of use

Among the total publications, 74 (68.9%) discuss individual /consumption products, mainly cars, cell phones and electronics (Table 2), 32 (43.3%) focusing on positive and negative emotions.

Unlike the individual /consumption products, collective products are the minority in the revised publications; 9 assignments (12.2%) approached collective public use products (Figure 2): 2 relating to web sites; 3, to street furniture, 1 pub-

lic installation and, the other 4, relating to environments, or public spaces (elevator, toll roads, waiting room and library). Among the urban furniture, a bus shelter and gym equipment (Pizzato et al. 2012a and 2012b); a speedometer (Dorrestijn and Verbeek, 2013); an example of persuasive technology for wellbeing (a behavior-influencing design for wellbeing); and a Jazz shower (Desmet and Pohlmeier, 2013): a public installation that plays jazz, where to really hear the music, the user has to stand directly underneath a showerhead-like speaker, which is designed to enhance the experience so that the user feels immersed in the music.

	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	Total	%
Publications	8	5	15	4	2	21	19	74	100
Positive	3	3	3	1		10	8	28	37,8
Negative					1	2	1	4	5,4
positive/ negative									
	5	1	11	2	1	8	4	32	43.3
Unspecified		1	1	1		1	6	10	13,5
consumption/individual	6	3	13	3	2	12	12	51	68,9
Collective	1	1	1			4	2	9	12,2
Others	1	1	1	1		5	5	14	18,9

Table 2. Emotions, products and publications focused on reviewed articles by year of publication

<p>WEB SITES</p>		
<p>SPEEDOMETER</p>		

Figure 2. Cited collective public products

As the systematic literature review indicates, there are few works about public-use products, aimed at serving collective care for such products. This lack could be explained by the great difficulty in identifying the needs of a variety of users and the development of a product where relations with users tend not to be as intense as those involved when a product is for exclusive use, as pointed out by Löbach (2001).

CONCLUSION

Since its emergence approximately fourteen years ago, the field of Design and Emotion has instigated research in several areas of knowledge, from different nationalities, relating the use of, or the experience with products to emotion. In order to assess the type of emotion related to different products under consideration, and primarily aiming at the treatment of products of collective public use, this article presents a review and an analysis of publications in international Design and Ergonomics journals in the 2007 to 2013 period.

In order to systematize the grouping of articles, they were classified according to usage: a group for products of individual or consumption use, another for collective use and others or unspecified. The emotion types were classified as follows: “positive” emotions, “negative”, “positive and negative”, and “unspecified” emotion. The mapping of the articles published reinforces the interdisciplinary field and confirms the promi-

nence of the Delft University of Science and Technology (forerunner of Design and Emotion), in publications in the field.

The research hypothesis that collective public use products do not usually take part in the search scope of Design and Emotion was confirmed. The result shows that the focus of the publications in Design and Ergonomics areas of knowledge is on the individual consumer products. In general, there is a clear inclination for a simultaneous approach of positive and negative emotions. In addition, the author shows little interest in the approach to negative emotions, which often interfere with the product user to the point of the user abolishing use and/ or developing a fear of using the product.

Hopefully, with the mapping and classification of the articles, this study can be considered a contribution to the development of Design and Emotion research, mainly by the suggestion of the defiant demand of work aimed at meeting the numerous human and collective needs that exist in our society, which in terms of sustainability, should contribute to a world of responsible consumption.

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EMPATHY EXPRESSION AND DEVELOPMENT IN INDUSTRIAL DESIGN EDUCATION

Fabio Andrés Téllez
North Carolina State University – College of Design
✉ fatellez@ncsu.edu

ABSTRACT

Empathy has been recognized as a fundamental ability to generate social cohesion, to facilitate conflict resolution, to foster collaboration, and to inhibit aggression. In the Design field, this ability is considered essential for designers to acquire a deep understanding of the users in order to develop products, services, and experiences that meet their needs. As a consequence, this research proposal aims to understand how empathy is expressed and developed by students in the context of an industrial design studio, through the understanding of its methodological, pedagogical and curricular conditions. The lack of literature exploring this phenomenon calls for a theory-building methodology such as grounded theory. In order to triangulate what students say, do, and make, this study proposes the use of semi-structured interviews applied to students and faculty members, participant observation of the design studio, and collection of students' portfolios (i.e. artifacts created by the students in the studio). The analysis of these data will provide evidence of students' expressions of empathy for the user, as well as evidence of the factors that might foster the development of this ability in an industrial design studio.

KEYWORDS: *empathy, empathy decline, human-centered design, design studio, design education, grounded theory, qualitative research*

INTRODUCTION AND PROBLEM DEFINITION

Empathy, the capacity to feel, recognize and understand other people's emotional and mental states, is considered one of the most important abilities for interacting in the social world. It provides the individual with the capacity of taking another's perspective in order to better and more deeply understand his/her thoughts, feelings, and circumstances, and to act accordingly. This ability has been directly associated with prosocial behavior—to act in a way that is beneficial to other people and society as a whole—and inversely correlated with aggression and narcissism. It is considered a trait of emotional intelligence, a precursor of healthy human relations, and a catalyst for civic engagement. In the Design field, empathy is considered an essential ability for acquiring a deep understanding of the users and, in turn, to develop products, services, and experiences that meet their needs. Through empathy, designers can move beyond their egocentric worldview and gain sensitivity towards the users, to relate to their experiences, and to demonstrate respect for them by recognizing and understanding their cognitive, emotional, physical, social, and cultural conditions. Thus, empathy can be considered an instrument to respectfully identify and satisfy people's needs through design, to solve interpersonal

differences through mutual understanding, and, in sum, to improve the quality and fluidity of human relations (Baron-Cohen & Wheelwright, 2004; Gerdes et al., 2011; Howe, 2013; Partnership for 21st Century Skills, 2003; Kouprie & Visser, 2009; Dandavate et al., 1996; Carroll et al., 2010; IDEO, 2011; Wiggins & McTighe, 2005; Liem & Sanders, 2013).

However, there is empirical evidence that points out a decline in empathy since the year 2000 among American college students. Konrath and colleagues (2011) conducted an analysis on 72 samples of students (N=13,737) who completed the Interpersonal Reactivity Index-IRI (a test frequently used to measure empathy) between 1979 and 2009, and found a significant decrease in Empathic Concern and Perspective Taking—two of the four components of the IRI—since 2000. In terms of percentiles, this decline means that, whereas the average student in 1979 could be located at the 50th percentile of the distribution of EC or PT, the average student in 2009 could be located at the 26th percentile of EC and the 33rd percentile of PT, which “represents a 48% decrease in EC and a 34% decrease in PT” (Konrath et al., 2011, p. 186).

Even though this decline in empathy cannot be generalized to the entire American population (since the studied samples correspond exclusively to college students), given the

importance of this ability, this situation calls for attention and intervention. In the Design field, this represents the opportunity to examine at what extent empathy is effectively being fostered through design education, and to explore how empathy emerges throughout the design process in order to identify the factors that foster or hinder its expression and development.

RESEARCH QUESTION

This paper synthesizes the researcher's dissertation proposal to study the described phenomenon in the context of an undergraduate Industrial Design studio, which aims to answer the following research questions:

1. Under what conditions do students' expressions of empathy for users emerge and develop?
 - 1.1. What attributes of the project definition can be associated with students' expressions of empathy?
 - 1.2. What design methods can be associated with students' expressions of empathy?
 - 1.3. What pedagogical aspects can be associated with students' expressions of empathy?
2. What aspects of the students' performance evidence their empathy for users?
 - 2.1. What attributes of design solutions provide evidence of students' empathy for users?
 - 2.2. Besides these attributes, how do students express their empathy for users?

WHAT IS EMPATHY?

The term *empathy* can be defined as the “ability to recognize other people's personality, emotional condition, beliefs and desires in order to make sense of, predict and anticipate their behaviour” (Howe, 2013, p. 9), and as the “ability to identify what someone else is thinking or feeling and to respond to their thoughts and feelings with an appropriate emotion” (Baron-Cohen, 2011, p. 16).

These definitions comprise two components: an affective and a cognitive response. The former refers to the unconscious recognition of another person's emotional states and the physical and emotional involuntary reactions triggered by those. The latter refers to the conscious process that allows the subject to understand and predict another person's feelings, thoughts, and behaviors through a cognitive process of taking another person's perspective (Goldstein & Michaels, 1985; Howe, 2013; Gerdes et al., 2011; Baron-Cohen & Wheelwright, 2004).

Additionally, decision-making is also considered a component of empathy, associated with the cognitive response. In this context, it can be defined as a subject's coherent reaction towards another person, after feeling and understanding his/her thoughts, feelings and circumstances. This means that an

inappropriate response triggered by another person's emotional state does not count as empathy (Baron-Cohen, 2011).

EMPATHY IN THE DESIGN FIELD

In accordance to the above definition, in the Design field, empathy is said to be present when the designer approaches the user and is able to gain an understanding of his/her thoughts, feelings and circumstances. This attention paid to the user is consistent with the tenets of different approaches to design, such as User Centered Design, Human Centered Design, or Empathic Design, which aim to develop new design solutions (i.e. products, services, experiences, systems) through a process that allows designers to acquire a cognitive and an affective understanding of the user, by gathering, analyzing, and interpreting information from his/her life. This allows the designer to gain insights into the user's life, and can reveal the user's need and desires in order to incorporate them into the design solution (Liem & Sanders, 2011; Steen, 2012; Postma et al., 2012; Suri, 2003; ISO, 2010; IDEO, 2011).

Empathy can also be found in the Design Thinking model proposed by the D.School (2010), where this ability is put as the first step of a human-centered design process, and where it is considered a fundamental characteristic of the designer's mindset. This model invites the designer to get to know the users, understand what they think, feel, need, and want, and to focus the design activity on them (D.School, 2010; Carroll et al., 2010; Plattner et al., 2012; Melles, et al. 2012).

TEACHING EMPATHY IN THE DESIGN STUDIO

Assuming that empathy is being incorporated as part of the skills that designers acquire throughout their higher education (a question that is addressed by the research study herein proposed), this would probably occur in the design studio, which plays a central role in introducing the students to the design culture and in conserving and transmitting the values of the design profession (Crawford, 2013; Salama, 1995).

The design studio is considered the “backbone” of most design programs around the world (Salama, 1995) and is characterized by the development of design projects with a constant interaction between the students and the instructor. For Brown & Adler (2008), this system is an example of a social learning environment, where students learn from the guidance of an established practitioner—who comments on and critiques their work—and from the feedback they receive from their fellow classmates (Anthony, 1991).

According to Goldman and colleagues (2012), this learning environment has the potential to foster empathy in students when the implemented design process is human-centered, since “they begin to move beyond egocentric views of the world and no longer design based on their own needs, desires, experiences or preferences (...) [but they] actively seek solutions to problems that meet the needs of others” (Goldman et al., 2012, p. 16).

THEORETICAL PERSPECTIVE

The purpose of this study to understand the expression and development of empathy in the specific context of design education, and the nature of the research questions herein presented, suggest the adoption of a naturalistic paradigm. This paradigm conceives multiple socially-built realities, values the interaction between the researcher and the phenomenon as a source of insights, acknowledges the researcher's values and theoretical positions, and praises the role of interpretation in the process of inquiry (Groat & Wang, 2002).

METHODOLOGY

The scarcity of literature that explores empathy in the context of design education suggests the use of a theory-building methodology to answer the proposed research questions. Consequently, this study will implement Grounded Theory, which is defined as a “systematic inductive, comparative, and interactive approach to inquiry” (Charmaz & Henwood, 2010, p. 241) that aims to build “middle-range theories”—applicable to real-world situations—based on empirical observations (Oktay, 2012).

This research strategy is characterized by using an approach to the studied phenomenon that is free of preconceptions, and an iterative process that comprises three main actions: Data Collection, Coding, and “Memoing”. These actions allow a progressive construction of theoretical ideas that evolve into a more structured theory (Groat & Wang, 2002).

Additionally, Grounded Theory is characterized by the study of phenomena in their natural contexts, the use of interpretation and finding of meaning to analyze data, the focus on the respondent's viewpoints, the use of multiple techniques to answer the research question, the holistic view of the context of study, the prolonged and intense contact with the studied phenomenon, and the role of the researcher as a “measurement device” (Groat & Wang, 2002; Denzin & Lincoln, 1998).

STUDY SITE AND PARTICIPANTS

This study will be performed in the undergraduate program of Industrial Design at the College of Design at North Carolina State University, and specifically in the fourth year studio that applies human-centered design methods. This scenario provides a semester-long human-centered design experience to up to 18 college students majoring in Industrial Design, and who are taught by a faculty member who guides their learning process through a series of projects, desk critiques, general critiques, and presentations. This setting was selected according to the following considerations:

- Design studios have the potential to foster empathy because they transmit the values of the design profession.

- A human-centered approach also has the potential to foster empathy since it invites the student to take the user's perspective.
- Design studios are long enough to allow a prolonged engagement and a persistent observation of the site, which favors the study's trustworthiness (Guba, 1981).
- The participants (college students and their instructor) are mature and mentally developed enough to adequately respond to interviews that explore their behaviors in the studio.
- As a PhD student at the College of Design at North Carolina State University, the researcher has open access to this context.

DATA COLLECTION, ANALYSES, AND INTERPRETATION

Following the proposed methodology (Grounded Theory), this study proposes data collection through semistructured interviews applied to the students and the professor, participant observation of the studio sessions, and revision of student portfolios (collection of the artifacts produced in the studio). These techniques provide a detailed view of what students and the instructors say, do, and make, in coherence with Elizabeth Sander's model to access people's experiences (Sanders, 2002).

In Grounded Theory, the process of data analysis (coding and memoing) starts early, occurs concurrently with the process of data collection, and is iterative. This process will start with the transcription of non-textual data (e.g. audio recordings), the coding of these transcriptions and field notes, and the production of analytical memos that allow the researcher to undertake an initial interpretation. Once theoretical saturation has been reached (when the data provides no further information) the emergent concepts will be classified in categories and more theoretical memos will be written with a more general and complete interpretation. These last two steps will provide the structure and content for the emergent theory aimed at answering the research questions.

EXPECTED RESULTS

The study herein proposed aims to add to the body of knowledge regarding design education and design research. By answering the proposed questions through the selected methodology, this study proposes to define some pedagogical, curricular, and methodological conditions required in an industrial design studio to foster the expression and development of empathy in the students. This study sets out to identify some of the attributes of a design solution that can be associated with the students' expression of empathy. Ultimately, the aim of this study is to provide design educators with empirically based knowledge to assess and adjust their practices

in order to continue fostering this fundamental and apparently declining ability.

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SUBTHEME 3 Methodological Issues of Design and Emotion

Methods for the detection, assessment and application and of human emotions.

Includes these topics:

- Trans-disciplinary Methodologies
- Co-creation and Participatory Design
- Persuasive Design and User Behavior
- Kansei Engineering
- Corporate Identity and Branding
- Retail Design

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APPRAISALS TO LIGHT: A FRAMEWORK TO STUDY EMOTION IN RETAIL SPACES

Bhakti Sharma

State University of New York College at Buffalo

✉ sharmab@buffalostate.edu

Leandro Mileto Tonetto

Universidade do Vale do Rio dos Sinos

Zooma – Consumer Experience

✉ ltonetto@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Appraisal Theory, developed in the Psychological Sciences, states that emotion is a result of people's appraisals regarding the effect of a situation over their well-being. The theory has been discussed in the current literature in its relation to design, specifically the design and emotion field. Through a literature review of the Theory and the methods of studying lighting and emotion, a methodological framework is discussed to understand the user's appraisals of lighted environment. Thus, the aim of this paper is to present and discuss a framework to understand the effect of lighting in retail stores on consumer's appraisals and, consequently, their emotions, to be used in research and lighting design projects. Retail environment lighting projects that focus on evoking or preventing certain kinds of emotional experiences might be understood and developed in this research tradition in order to understand if the intended experience was achieved or not.

KEYWORDS: *design and emotion; emotional design; appraisal theory; lighting design; research methods. communication, graphic design.*

INTRODUCTION

Space and architecture fill the experiential voids in the users' lives and provide a collective/shared experience for them. The Standardized Mass Produced Economy, and consequently the Built Space have come a long way since the Industrial Revolution. As Klingmann (2007) states, the key focus of architecture has shifted from 'one size fits all' to 'customization-for-all' economy in today's market.

In a world where brands are ubiquitous, and users have an ever-evolving awareness of the brands, it is imperative for the companies to have a strong spatial presence, one that is clearly distinguishable from the established visual identity. The experience that is created through a stronger visual space, where the primary function is to connect with the user, distinguishes one brand from the other and makes it unique from visual identity. The corporate or retail space, an experiential environment, is the most comprehensive expression of brand culture (Bowen, 1998).

The brands are constantly reinventing the new marketplace or the shrine-like quality that retail spaces are being associated with; this shrine-like quality of brands having a direct connection with its users and their emotions. Many factors

including spatial expression, sculptural quality, sounds, merchandize etc. serve as stimuli that affect the emotions and ultimately the behavior of the users. As Baker et al (1992) point out, according to various studies in the field of retail environment, various parameters including ambient conditions, social variables, and design factors have been studied.

Other studies have included the addition of human variable to the retail environment by Turley (2000). Thus, in this paper, the authors discuss the use of a methodological frameworks to develop research and lighting design projects to evoke or prevent intended emotions, based on Psychological literature, specifically Appraisal Theory.

STUDY OF LIGHTING IN RETAIL ENVIRONMENT

The retail environment is a high-stimulus environment and one such dominant variable that is closely related to the ambient conditions is the lighting of the space. 'Literature indicates that lighting can influence emotions, mood and cognition as well as atmosphere and spatial impressions, although at times the collected findings are inconclusive' (Custers, 2010, pp.331-343).

The lighting industry typically designs to achieve a desired effect for an interior space (Davis, 2011). Several studies are available to assess different parameters of lighting, and several other parameters are available to assess the effect of lighting on human emotion. However, as Davis suggests, the depth and wealth of our research and knowledge of the impact of lighting on visual task performance only underscores the dearth of information on the other aspects of human response to lighting.

The lighting literature available that is helpful in understanding portions of the effect of lighting on human emotional response, and subsequently on environmental cognition, is incomplete without the discussion of studies by John Flynn (1973). Flynn recorded changes to subjective human impressions when the lighting stimuli altered in various architectural settings. Flynn linked lighting changes to various impressions such as spaciousness, visual clarity, privacy, pleasantness, relaxation and complexity. These subjective impressions were closely related to modes in Flynn's experiment. Flynn suggested that the continuum of changes between extremes of these attributes – bright/dim; uniform/non-uniform; central/perimeter; and warm/cool – helped the designers in creating the desired lighting environment. For example, a designer could use non-uniform luminance to create related subjective impressions of pleasantness, sociability, interest etc. Such is the example of separating people visually in a crowded space by using lighting when it is hard to do so physically—a technique often used in cocktail lounges, fine restaurants, and reception rooms. Flynn's study is considered seminal to this day and uses a semantic differential scale to understand the brightness, contrast, and color aspects of lighting, as well as the related subjective impressions of pleasantness, public character, spaciousness, and relaxed nature.

Other studies investigating the effect of spatial and lighting conditions on human psychology have been smaller scale studies directly related to a certain architectural market sector. Fostervold's (2008) study of proportion of direct and indirect lighting on the cognitive performance of office workers tackles the topic of glare and discusses its relation to stress levels at work. The variables assessed were subjective symptoms, subjective well being, and cognitive performance, which enabled data to be gathered on the effect of four ceiling-mounted lighting schemes, which provide different combinations of well-being and cognitive performance related to direct and indirect lighting in ordinary office environments. Boyce's (2003) study of office environments discussed in detail the effects of luminance distribution, non-task surface luminance, and control over lighting on various behavioral outcomes. In Boyce's study lighting professionals prepared questionnaires and observed users under the lighted environment.

Custers et al's (2010) study of lighting in retail environments studies fashion retail shops, and using descriptive appraisal mechanisms concludes that lighting has a potential contribution to perceived ambiance but is only one of numerous elements that may play a role. Three categories of variables – shop interiors, lighting attributes, and perceived atmosphere were assessed and quantified independently by different raters.

Other approaches to studying subjective impressions of a space have included the paired comparisons and semantic differential scaling as employed by Houser (2003) and his team to assess subjective responses to linear fluorescent direct/indirect lighting systems. In a commentary about the said method, Newsham (2003) from the Institute for Research in Construction, Canada, expresses his concern about the several underlying concepts that emerge from semantic differential analysis.

Veitch and Newsham's (2008) study of task performance and the effect of lighting on physiology studies the parameters of brightness, visual attraction, and complexity at a larger scale. The study uses the theory of Linked Mechanisms by David Wyon to tie the different parameters of lighting together. Basically, the approach that employs regression analysis develops a set of links between the lighting features and the routes to worker performance, health, and organizational productivity. Wyon (1996) describes linked mechanisms as elements in built environments that have an effect on behavioral outcomes. For instance, luminance distribution, non-task surface luminance, control over lighting, and other similar variables are 'linked' to the users' behavioral outcomes. Regression analysis that examines whether the influence of one variable (X) on another (Y) is partly or wholly explained by the influence of X on a third variable (M), and the influence of M on Y is the statistical method used in this study.

In the field of subjective impressions in retail lighting, a recent study by Schielke (2010) investigates the effect of lighting in corporate communication. For this study, computer visualizations of retail outlets with different lighting variations were evaluated in terms of light, spatial setting, and brand impression using the semantic differential technique, a method of quantifying a stimulus and subjective reactions on a scale.

In the above-mentioned literature, synthesized in Table 1, the study of lighting has been isolated to a market typology i.e. office, retail, commercial, and it has been limited within the parameters that have been studied.

As the reader can see in Table 1, distinct lighting attributes are evaluated in different lighting studies. As most lighting practitioners and researchers would agree, ignoring any one of the facets of lighting design would not constitute an accurate study of the subject. John Flynn's approach to lighting design is still the benchmark of understanding subjective impressions as it tackles the issues of brightness, contrast, and color – the three closely related qualities of light. Another quality of light that may easily change from sparkle to glare depending on observer's subjective impression, thereby causing a physiological and psychological reaction, should be studied. However, the understanding of subjective impressions is another study that cannot be undertaken in isolation without studying the inherent affect, emotions, and the appraisals of these emotions. For this reason the study must consider brightness, contrast, color and directionality (glare) in the development of a framework in order to understand the relations between light and emotion.

Study	Space attributes		Lighting attributes			
	Related Space	Visual Attraction of Space	Brightness	Contrast	Color	Directionality (Glare/ Sparkle)
Flynn	General		X	X	X	
Boyce	Office					X
Custers	Retail	X	X			X
Houser	Office		X	X		
Veitch/Newsham	Office		X			X
Schielke	Retail	X			X	
Proposed Framework	General		X	X	X	X

Table 1: Synthesis of lighting attributes studied in the current literature and the proposed framework. Source: The Authors

When referring to emotions, we usually mean all the affective phenomena that help us to understand and deal with life, connecting us to or pushing us away from people, things, events and actions (Frijda, 1986). Some examples are love, hate, desire, disgust, and fear.

In the following section we focus on Appraisal Theory, one of the most widely adopted theories of emotion, and also the basis for the discussed framework.

APPLYING APPRAISAL THEORY TO DESIGNING WITH LIGHT

In the cognitive tradition of emotion research, appraisals are understood as the cause of emotions. Appraisal Theory states that appraisals are evaluations from people regarding the effect of an event or situation (including retail spaces) over their well-being, as potentially beneficial or harmful (Arnold, 1960). In the appraisal tradition, it is understood that the way someone processes the information regarding an event causes and determines the emotion, rather than the event itself (Lazarus, 1991).

In terms of lighting, a wash of diffuse light in a retail space creates a more uniform light, and thus has the potential to make you feel comfortable and assist you in making your selection of merchandise. An expected emotional response could be your evaluation about the space making you feel softened and relaxed. On the other hand, a high-contrast environment with pockets of bright and dark areas, and display areas marked with sparkle and focal glow in a huge space crowded with stimuli (clothes, e.g.), could make you feel confused and cause difficulty in concentrating and focusing on what you are looking for, causing irritation or disappointment. Both examples are based on the authors' professional experience. Thus, these responses are likely to change if for various consumer types who experience similar situations. For example, consumers that enjoy the drama that lighting creates may feel bored and disinterested in a uniform environment.

These examples go against the mainstream idea in lighting studies that the events and places themselves are more meaningful than what people capture from and see in them. Every market segment, or consumption group, with their cultural and psychological characteristics, tend to understand the environment in a different way.

If a professional wishes to develop a lighting project that causes a specific and intended effect at the emotional level, they must pay attention to how the target responds to a variety of stimuli and to what generally causes, to these specific kinds of people, the intended experience. Appraisals mediate products and emotions, and ultimately reasons why different people experience different emotions when appraising the same product (Scherer, 1984; Hekkert and Desmet, 2007).

Appraisal Theory has been explored in its relation to design (Demir, Desmet and Hekkert, 2009). "Emotional Design" is a design field concerned with either evoking or preventing certain emotions. Lighting projects focusing on causing or avoiding certain kinds of emotional experiences might be understood and developed in this research tradition.

In psychology, this research tradition based on the analysis of appraisals has at least two clear different approaches, defined as thematic and componential, named in Smith and Lazarus (1990) as "molar" and "molecular".

The thematic approach treats appraisals as summary statements reflecting the general meaning of a situation to a person. It is defined as an appraisal theme. Lazarus (1991) states that each discrete emotion, e.g. sadness or joy, is connected to a different overall meaning, e.g. irrevocable loss or progress towards realization of a goal, respectively.

The componential approach does not understand appraisals as unidirectional. It describes them as a result from distinct questions, each one focusing on a different aspect of the situation (Roseman, 2001; Scherer, 2001). The people's response to each one of these questions composes the appraisal components. They are described and discussed in their relation to lighting issues, as follows.

Motive Consistency

How does the space and the lighting of an environment relate to the consumer's motives to visit a particular store? This would be the main question related to motive consistency, and it is related not just to the functional characteristics of a retail space, but also to its effect over the person's needs, concerns, or goals, regarding self-expression or social symbolism. Positive answers tend to be connected to positive emotions. For instance, when a consumer first arrives at a luxury retail store and sees focal glow created by focused lights on a mannequin wearing a cocktail dress, the consumer in our example is looking for self-gratification and luxury. In this process, the consumer might feel joy and satisfaction while admiring the dress and ultimately purchasing it. We can say that the appraisal is the consumer's thought that the product is exclusive and luxurious, and it relates to the consistency of the purchase motive (self-gratification). The emotional effects are joy and satisfaction.

Research on this target might be used in design briefs. In order to create joy and satisfaction to jewelry consumers looking for self-gratification and luxurious experiences, the lighting designer may use different lighting techniques such as the one described above on the most exquisite and exclusive pieces.¹

Intrinsic Pleasantness

To what extent is the lighted environment pleasant to the consumer? Intrinsic pleasantness is about the sensorial dimension and its adaptation to the situation. Pleasantness is usually connected to emotions like desire (positive), whilst unpleasantness is often related to emotions like disgust (negative). As an example, a playful color-changing LED display behind the showcase window for a teddy bear may make a child interested even more in a toy, causing fascination or admiration (emotional response), due to the thought that it is funnier and more dynamic than the others (appraisal). On the other hand, an excessively bright light above a restaurant table can be the cause of irritation and alarm (emotional response), due to disability glare and subsequently may create the thought in the customer's mind that the space is poorly planned (appraisal).

Considering the first example, a design brief can identify colorful and intermittent lights as the keys to designing a display that causes emotions like fascination or admiration among kids. These would be the parameters that a lighting designer would use to manipulate lighting to achieve an intended emotional response in a retail environment.

Expectation Confirmation

To what extent does the space and the lighting of the environment meet the consumer's expectation? The appraisal is a confirmation or a violation of a person's expectations, which ranges from unexplored aspects of the space to the conse-

1. It is important to highlight that all examples are fictional and refer to the authors' experiences and retail design projects.

quence of an action by the person when in the place. For example, an excessively illuminated pub in diffused fluorescent lamps may create an environment similar to an office—an effect that may lead people to think they are not allowed to relax when drinking alcoholic beverages (appraisal). The resulting emotions can be contempt towards the place, as well as alarm regarding their own behavior, and ultimately result in an environment that is not conducive to social interaction.

In order to avoid people being alarmed and too conscious about their own behavior, and also the contempt regarding a pub that does not provide the relaxing atmosphere they want, a lighting design brief should emphasize diffuse and low lighting.

Standards Conformance

How does the space and the lighting of the environment relate to standards the consumer is used to? The response can be a confirmation or a violation. Every different condition will be processed and understood differently by distinct types of consumers. For instance, when a consumer goes to a low-end store to buy a new pair of shoes, if the lighting of the display is high-contrast, rich, and creates an ambience of luxury, the consumer may mistake the store to be high-end and the said product to be out of his buying power (appraisal), thus resulting in emotions such as embarrassment and contempt.

The reader might be thinking at the moment that this example could be related to other appraisal components, like intrinsic pleasantness, and of course it is. We are highlighting it as an example of standards conformance both to show that the same element can be related to more than one appraisal component, and that the standards that people are used to dealing with also tend to interfere in their evaluation. In the mentioned example, the resulting emotion shows that overcoming expectations is not always desirable and this fact should be considered in design briefs.

Certainty Component

How certain is the user about the timeless quality of the stimuli for the future? Uncertainty is usually connected to fear and hope, and certainty to happiness and sadness.

The immaterial characteristic of light makes this appraisal component indicative of a peripheral interest in lighting studies and design briefs. Since the lighting stimulation is usually limited in time to consumers, from the studied appraisal components, this is the one that has shown the weekly potential to help understanding user's appraisals and emotions to lighted environments. It is important to highlight, at this point, that this is expected and easily understood, since the appraisal components discussed here are based on experience with products (Demir, Desmet and Hekkert, 2009).

Agency

Who or what is a responsible agency for a given situation, according to the user's opinion? It can be the person, or a

parameter of the space such as lighting, or it could also be the situation. This is the usual question employed to represent the agency component. In lighting studies, it is natural to think that the most common answer will make reference to the environment/situation. The agency component of appraisals therefore, would be the lighting itself. For example, an office lighted with a task lamp over the table and no peripheral lighting may give people a headache when they look up from their visual display terminals. The designer, on the other hand, when reading results from a study with this kind of result, should be critical enough to understand that it is a design problem, not a user problem. In the previous example, the addition of peripheral lighting will not only solve the problem of strained eyes, but will also create the subjective impression of a larger room. The resulting emotion from the given situation tends to be different, facing the two mentioned conditions. It could be anger (not a self-directed emotion), realizing that the space was poorly planned, or frustration (self-directed emotion), by thinking that the resulting lack of concentration is their fault..

Although on a psychological level it might be interesting to understand these changes, at a design level it may sound uninteresting. All user problems are design issues and project challenges. That is the reason why we consider “agency” another appraisal component of interest in lighting studies.

Coping Potential

Can one understand and mitigate the harmful effect of lighting in the particular space, if that is the case? It is about the user’s (perceived) ability to deal with the undesired adverse aspects of a situation. The intent of the lighting of the space should be to give a perceived control on the environment to the users. A lack in coping abilities can result in emotions like anger or dissatisfaction, whilst a trust in their own ability can lead people to feel confident and satisfied. We would like to ratify that every point-of-view is a world of its own, and that every kind of consumer/person will tend to appraise life situations in distinct ways, leading to different emotional responses to the same events:

If the same situation causes different emotional responses it follows that this situation was appraised differently. Thus, the necessity hypothesis does not allow for factors other than appraisals to determine different emotional reactions toward the same situation (Siemer, Mauss and Gross, 2007, p.593).

This dynamic relation between reality, appraisals and emotion makes us think that the relation between people and design is multidimensional. Although both approaches – thematic and componential – can be useful in emotion research, the thematic approach might be too general to be applied to lighting studies, since themes such as “the progress towards the realization of a goal”, will make it difficult to describe lighting design briefs, due to the lack of specificity. Since the componential approach is multifaceted, although less holistic than describing human experience, we believe it is more adequate to elaborate both lighting design briefs and research on the topic.

RESEARCH ON APPRAISALS: METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

After having discussed the literature behind lighting in retail environments and appraisal theory, this paper now discusses a general framework to be applied to lighting studies, or, more specifically, what is defined here as appraisals to light studies. In a two-part approach, this paper first discusses the kind of theoretical approach that is more suitable to these studies – thematic or componential. And then in the second part, a methodological approach focusing on research methods is discussed.

The “appraisals to light” approach: Theoretical basis

The discussion made on Appraisal Theory suggests that the componential approach might be more suitable to lighting studies, since it provides more useful information on how to develop lighting design projects focused on user’s emotions. The approach understands appraisals as multidirectional, describing them as a result from distinct questions (Roseman, 2001; Scherer, 2001); hence the reason why it seems more suitable to lighting studies. Two fictional examples, focusing on the same appraisal component and on the same retail space, are given to make the point clearer. Applying the same situation to a fashion retail store, one with a lighting design that aims at creating a subjective impression of a luxury store, the following two situations help us understand the approach better.

- Situation A: A male shopper in the said retail environment is looking for a new suit. His motives are related to self-gratification and social expression, and the environment is appraised as luxurious, exclusive and worth visiting. The emotional outcome is arousal and pleasantness.
- Situation B: Another male shopper in the same retail environment is in the store for a new suit as well. However, his motive is more utilitarian, and his idea of luxury is more connected to the quality of the product rather than the experience itself. The environment is appraised as selfish and futile. The emotional outcomes are arousal and unpleasantness.

None of these men have the ‘right’ perception about the lighting, and they can represent distinct consumer groups. It is not for the end user to have the ‘right’ perception about the lighting or the subjective impression that it creates. The retailer should set the target and know which are the right lighting attributes to reinforce the perception of luxury for that particular target group. Emotion psychology brings the idea that different kinds of people can have completely different perceptions and emotions when facing the same scenarios (Arnold, 1960; Lazarus, 1991; Scherer, 1984). This is the case in the above examples.

Following the componential approach, as mentioned above (please, note that the example given is only about one of the seven appraisal components), during an interview in a re-

search project the researcher needs to understand the consumer's motives when attending the store and how particular lighting characteristics relate to them. The information from the research seems to have a greater potential to be applied in lighting design projects, since it gives more specific content to the designer, making it easier to work on the project.

On the other hand, by following the simpler path, the thematic approach, the researcher would, in the data collection, investigate how consumers feel in that environment. The answers could be vague, for example, "it looks nice"; "it is luxurious, I like it"; "it is welcoming". The question is: Would this information be useful? Probably not. This is the reason why the componential approach seems to offer more than the thematic approach to lighting design projects.

The "appraisals to light" approach: Methodological approach

From a design perspective, lighting projects should start by defining the brand attributes to be reinforced among people in retail stores. "Architecture is supposed to shape 'corporate identity', which is also expressed in company logos, websites and merchandise. Nothing is excluded from this policy. As suggested by Koojiman & Sierksma (2007), each brand must have its own easily identifiable architecture with distinctive colours, materials and profile". As the authors explore the relation between brand and retail architecture in their paper, they discuss how they instill the brand further into the consumer through the space and other supporting literature, in discussions by Pine and Gilmore (1999) and Koolhaas (1977).

As Brandston (2008) comments, "light, like music, fills, reveals and creates space." In order to tie the impressions, a brand wishes to create in the user's mind using the space, the space needs to be defined according to the brand and as a parameter, and lighting should define the space.

The designer should then define the subjective impressions that they wish to be created among the shoppers through the lighting. Assuming that as the most common practice, the appraisals to light approach follows the same path, and the second stage would be to investigate, among the target audience, which kind of lighting condition is more likely to evoke or prevent the intended emotions; one that is most beneficial for the brand and is true to the brand's identity.

To understand how an emotional phenomenon can be evoked, qualitative/exploratory research seems to be the best choice, since it focuses on understanding certain stimuli in depth, rather than mapping them objectively (Malhotra & Peterson, 2001). Thus, semi-structured interviews and focus groups, in which photos and videos of retail stores are used, might be the best choices to understand how a specific target group reacts to each kind of lighting scenario, and will increase understanding of how to recreate those reactions in real life. Participatory observation in real market situations can also be useful, even though this method is more demanding and less environmentally controlled by the researcher as it is hard

to identify the participants' ethnicity and gender quantitatively and this may affect the study.

In this process (for in-depth interviews or focus groups), an appraisal interview guide would help the researcher to conduct the data collection. The questions would be based on images of distinct lighting scenarios chosen to understand how to trigger the intended emotions. The questions would be focused on each one of the investigated lighting scenarios (pictures and videos during interviews), and would be elaborated to cover the appraisal components. Questions about motive consistency for a brand that intends to evoke the emotion 'inspiration', could be:

1. What are your motivations when you are looking for products of this specific brand?
2. Look at a picture of a lighted space. How does this environment help (or not) you find what you are looking for in the store?
3. How does this lighting relate (negatively or positively) to what you want?
4. What comes to your mind when you look at the picture?
5. How do you feel about it?

If the answers to questions 1-5 are not connected to the intended emotion – inspiration in this case – the interviewer should ask: Does it look inspiring to you? Why? How should it be to look inspiring? Which one(s) of the other pictures/videos that you have seen would you say is the most inspiring?

By analyzing the content of answers for the seven appraisal components, the researcher/ lighting designer would have a broad range of information to design to evoke the emotion inspiration, leading to the third and last stage: experimentation.

Experiments on design usually manipulate certain variables (independent variables), in order to check their effect over other ones (dependent variables) in a quantitative way, by using structured questionnaires (Christensen, 1989). Common independent variables, in lighting studies, will be brightness, contrast, color and directionality (glare or sparkle). The dependent variable(s) will be the intended brand's emotional associations (in the mentioned example, inspiration).

From the second stage, the researcher/lighting designer can build lighting scenarios (either using digital image, 3D, or real retail stores), and develop experiments to test which of these conceptual scenarios is more adequate to evoke the brand's intended emotions.

In order to evaluate the dependent variables (consumer response), measurement scales must be used that expose the causality relation between dependent and independent variables. Some of the most common in this context will be five-to nine-point agreement scales (towards affirmative and negative sentences elaborated about the evaluated scenarios), and semantic differential scales (which consist in positioning a characteristic/word, e.g. 'love', at the left side of the paper, and, at the right side, its antonym, e.g. 'hate', and the respon-

dents are then encouraged to position their opinion between the words).²

From the second stage, the researcher/lighting designer can build lighting scenarios (either using digital image, 3D, or real retail stores), and develop experiments to test which of these conceptual scenarios is most adequate to evoke the brand's intended emotions.

CONCLUSION

The main goal of the study is to introduce and discuss a methodology for appraisal of lighting in a retail environment. A literature review of existing studies on the subjective analysis of lighting revealed the need for a holistic framework for studying the appraisal of lighting, one that captures the four key dimensions of lighting – brightness, color, contrast, and directionality. Space and its effect on branding is a discussion that is incomplete without the understanding of the subjective impressions it has on the users of the space. The analysis of literature revealed the need for a focus area of study of subjective impression covering various parameters of lighting applicable to various architectural spatial settings.

Appraisal Theory allows emotional design applied to lighting to evoke or restrict a certain emotion. The lighting design of a space and its parameters—brightness, color, contrast, and directionality—may be studied according to various appraisal components. This project's next steps will be to develop empirical studies based on this framework: defining brand attributes and intended emotions to be evoked in retail spaces (step 1), investigating how to trigger them in qualitative research (step 2), and experimenting with designed insights to evaluate the real potential of the designed lighting projects to evoke particular emotions (step 3).

It is crucial to highlight that the third step – experimentation – is a 'must do' stage in lighting studies, since it is the only procedure that will verify if user reactions are what we intend them to be. Other than that, it is common in the psychological literature that people find it difficult to report the actual causes of emotions, and the qualitative research proposes this type of investigation.

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SENSORIAL GROUPS AS A TOOL TO INTEGRATE THE EMOTIONAL DIMENSION IN DESIGN

Deyanira Bedolla Pereda

Autonomous Metropolitan University - Cuajimalpa

✉ dbedolla@correo.cua.uam.mx

ABSTRACT

Designing products that satisfy consumers requires information gathered through the human senses. This paper presents a “multisensory guideline for design”, a new tool proposed for emotional product design. These guidelines were based on the identification and study of human sensorial preference groups, and how they relate to the aesthetic qualities of products.

In order to integrate this tool in the design process, we have identified different human sensorial groups and ten aspects or attributes associated with the characteristics and peculiarities that can be used to design a product. The association of ten sensorial attributes with the sensorial groups made possible the integration of the “multisensory guidelines for design”.

The guidelines were tested using one product (computer mouse), focusing on one sense and a human sensorial group, and the evaluation was carried out by presenting three different models and control samples to 55 different users.

KEYWORDS: *Sensorial groups; emotions, senses, tools for design*

INTRODUCTION

Designing products to satisfy consumers requires information gathered through the human senses. Human senses can be seen as part of a structure, which determines the physical and psycho-emotional interaction the user has with an object. The senses involve a complete set of innate and learned psychological responses that can be graded, and which allow living beings to connect with the surrounding environment and interpret stimuli in order to react to and survive in their natural environment.

The senses allow the user to live, experiment and, as a result, evaluate their experience with both the environment and products. “Sensory systems allow people to perceive a product and assess what kind of product it is. They provide feedback on people’s actions. Furthermore, they tell a person whether a sensation (visual, auditory, tactual, olfactory, or gustatory) is pleasurable or should be avoided” (Schiffenstein, Hekkert, 2008, p. 3). Therefore, the sensorial systems are the structures and processes that determine customer’s preferences.

Sensorial science started to be developed when the importance of understanding sensorial phenomena was recog-

nized. It links scientific and technological disciplines that are concerned with sensorial perceptions and their relation to products like food, viticulture, cosmetics, car production and other industrial objects such as household and office products (Daban, 2002). This permits the development of a new generation of industrial products.

Some works focused on the analysis of the product experience (Schiffenstein & Hekkert, 2008) and the human emotional aspect in the product design (Norman 2004); (Jordan 2002) consider directly and indirectly the presence and relevance of the human senses. They are explained based on the reception and processing of the information levels provided by the object to the user through the senses and at the same time with the sensorial election code elements, considered determinant in the present work.

Another study in the field of product design, called Kansei Engineering (also known as Emotion Engineering) was proposed by Nagamichi (1988), who mentioned the importance of taking into account the desirable features of the product perceived by the end users through their senses. A few examples of how this methodology may be used in product development can be found in: (Schüte, *et al.*, 2008, Kyungmee, Changrim 2007, Lee, *et al.*, 2008).

Some companies and designers have already developed research that conceives of and explores several methods to introduce product desirable features perceived by users through their senses. This research seeks to identify the affective preferences and the emotional perceptions of the user. The research conceives of methodologies based on the attainment of adjectival descriptions, of expert and non-expert subjects (or customers) of the tested products.

For instance, Renault carried out experiments that include the tactile sensations behind the steering wheel (Crochemore & Nesa, 2004) and the car brake systems (Dairou *et al.*, 2010), Crochemore and Nesa (2004), used “Cartography of the preferences” and (Dairou *et al.*, 2003) “flash profile” (derived of the Free Choice Profiling from the field of sensorial evaluation of food) as a preliminary study to research the feasibility of the car brake systems description. On the other hand, Peugeot basically studies seats and dashboards (Egoroff, 2005) using the “hierarchical sorting task”. Cosmetics (Coronel *et al.*, 2003) and phones (Lorbo *et al.*, 2003) have also been re-evaluated by similar methodologies.

Regarding the marketing process, sensorial marketing (Rieuner, 2002) was presented on sales points as part of the experiential marketing trend. It evokes emotions via stimulation of the five senses by attributes that are complimentary to the product (fragrances, music, images).

Even though the sensorial approach, as a theme, has been partially developed, there are specific areas that can be explored.

In this article we propose a tool named multisensory guidelines for design (Bedolla, 2002) for product design based on users’ preferences, derived from their senses. These guidelines are based on the human sensorial group identification and study, based on research related to physiology and human perception psychology and how the group relates to the product’s aesthetic qualities meaning the different sensorial features of the product.

These guidelines allow the designer to:

- Meet the specific emotional and functional requirements of different and defined user groups.
- Know the specific sensorial attributes to apply to the products, satisfying the particular emotional and functional requirements of different groups of users recognized in the guidelines.
- Have a tool to complement the existing methods of contemporary design.

GUIDELINES FOR MULTISENSORY DESIGN: THE PRELIMINARY STUDIES

Human senses can be seen to be the structures that determine the physical and psycho-emotional interaction a user has with an object. Initially, the information reaches the sense organs (eyes, nose, ears and skin). The information is then delivered to the central nervous system and, eventually,

to the brain cortex. In the latter region, the individual makes her first pleasurable judgment based on the quality of the interaction (the use of different sensorial modalities) and its intensity (the impetus of the perception) (Guirao, 1980; Bermejo, 1981). This then continues through the limbic system and is channeled through other innate preferences as well as the memory. These determine the affective/cognitive evaluation the user makes as a result of the interaction with the object.

Therefore emotion is the dynamic syncopation of different cognitive and biological appreciations. Sensorial perception can be understood as the first filter in the emotional chain, which will eventually be transformed into more complex feelings and desires (Ortony *et al.*, 1996).

The Human Sensorial Groups

Based on the principle that senses allow the user to live, experiment and, as a result, evaluate the products, we studied the human sensorial perceptual process. By analyzing the perceptual process we identified the existence of determining factors which establish the sensorial capacities, and the individual differences in terms of preference for sensory information and the level of stimulation in the different human groups.

According to research related to physiology and human perception psychology, the different capacities, requirements, preferences and psycho-emotional demands of human groups will depend on a series of dimensions that comprise the person entirely (Bermejo, 1981; Buck & Buck, 1984; Plutchik, 1985; Rusell, Woudzia, 1986; Fernández, 1999). The first group of these dimensions belongs to the human’s internal boundary (related to the human’s organic component), and the second group belongs to the person’s external boundary (related to the environment where a person lives) (Munari, 1995; Quarante 1992). The dimensions of the internal boundary comprise the person’s personality tendency, gender, and age. The dimensions of the external boundary comprise the person’s culture, society, family, the raising environment, and the daily environment.

Based on these studies the human sensorial groups were classified as follows:

- **Four age groups:** the elderly, adults, adolescents and children (Craig, 1992; Goebel, 1981; Tyler, 1975). The age of the person determines the stage of development of the sensorial system (nervous system and peripheral sense organs), as well as physiological and psycho emotional demands. The physical and emotional sensory requirements are common to all the age groups determined by elements of their physiological nature and emotional being. However, the degree of their physiological nature and emotional being which determines the capacities and sensorial requirements according to the age of the individual will be diverse.
- **Two personality groups:** introverted and extroverted. These are determined by innate temperament and seem to depend on the nervous system. Introversion and extroversion require different kinds of sensorial stimulation. The

level demanded will depend on the degree of introversion or extroversion of the users. Even if all people have some elements of both personality groups, the individual tends to have more of one of them and to react according to these characteristics in certain situations, more than with other personality tendencies (Sheldon, 1970; Kretschmer, 1970; Eysenck, 2006).

- **Two gender groups:** women and men. Gender responds to physiological processes such as hormones and other organic processes. Women usually have sharper senses, except for sight, and develop a more sensitive nervous system. Biological differences can also be accentuated by the affections, stereotypes, and the different social roles determined by gender. However, these social roles are diversifying in response to economic and socio-cultural changing norms (Burg & Hulbert, 1961; Clark & Mehl, 1971; Baker, 1987; Hyde, 1995).

HUMAN GENDER					
Female			Male		
Visual	Sensorial	Requirements	Visual	Sensorial	Requirements
Females have twice the ability of the males to recognize and distinguish surface qualities of the objects, especially the light reflection or gloss. This characteristic can be applied to products conceived for this human group considering surface qualities such as glowing colour or polished surfaces.			Males have two times less ability than females in recognizing and distinguishing surface qualities of objects, especially the light reflection or gloss. This characteristic can be applied to products conceived for this human group, using opaque or dull colours.		
Tactile	Sensorial	Requirements	Tactile	Sensorial	Requirements
In general the tactile perceptions of this group are very high. They are especially sensitive to vibration and tactile pressure. These characteristics can be applied to products made of smooth textures.			The tactile perceptions of this group are less than the females, especially in the area of vibration. These characteristics can be applied to products considered the most easily identifiable bold textures, such as grainy, rough or corrugated.		

Table 1. Examples of the sensorial requirements of the gender groups
Source: Bedolla (2002)

The Sensorial Attributes

The study of how human sensorial groups relate to aesthetic qualities, as mentioned, seeks to recognize how different sen-

social features, when applied to object design, are capable of satisfying different user groups' preferences.

Considering the manufactured object we identified its sensorial features as the key elements that define its characteristics and uses (Manzini, 1993). Its sensorial features being those humans can perceive (Gimeno, 1986).

Therefore we have identified ten aspects or attributes associated with the characteristics and peculiarities of the different sensorial human groups. These attributes are visual: form, color and graphics; tactile: form, temperature, texture, weight and movement; olfactory: odors; and auditory – ambient sounds and music. Each one of the attributes has a specific effect on the user, which allows human sensorial requirements and characteristics to be satisfied.

There are specific effects we identified studying several researches to each attribute. The emotional effects of the visual attributes as the form and the decorative graphics are explained mainly in agreement with diverse authors (Sander *et al.*, 1969; Gombrich, 2000; Arnheim, 2004). Because our perceptive system is based on laws or mental superstructures, it stands out that the Gestalt theory of expression that is based on the principle of the isomorphism, supposes that a relation between the physical forces of the observed object exists: form, size, movement, etc., also the psychic dynamics of the observer, so that the features of the form influence in many ways the conduct and mood of the observer.

Moreover, a number of papers concerning colours (Goethe, 2006; Kandinsky, 2001; Ferrer, 1999) have progressed a theory that these stimulants produce certain physiological effects in individuals, due to physiological aspects. Just as the constitution of the human visual perception process of colours — with the central participation of the nervous system — in the same form produces certain psychological effects due to the element of nature, kingdom, body or substance that is always presented in indestructible association with the colour. These characteristics of the colours are going to allow them contemporarily to have important emotional and physical benefits for a person.

In relation to tactile features, it has been shown that they have a positive influence on both the mental and physical health of the user through the skin by means of the expression of texture, temperature, the weight and other elements that relate in an important way to the senses, like the movement, the pressure and the form through the objects, (Oñativia, 1972).

Auditory features are basically transmitted through vibrations. These create a physiological effect that enables the user to synchronize with the object, producing some physiological transformations (reduction or production of anxiety, high or low respiratory and cardiac rates, reduction or elevation of the sanguineous tension, and the reduction of stress hormones, among others) (Tomatis, 1978, 1991). Psychologically these effects are explained because the auditory information is received from the environment in several levels of abstraction and meaning, which also acquires certain impli-

EXTROVERT TENDENCIES			
General Sensorial Characteristics	Sensorial Features	Sensorial Features Involved	Expressed In the Product
<p>Tendency to seek strong sensorial stimuli. Strong nervous system, high threshold. They need more energy to appreciate sensorial stimuli.</p> <p>Less receptive if relaxed and more receptive if active or positively stressed.</p> <p>Seekers of sensation and new stimuli.</p>	<p>They prefer and are more sensitive to colors than shapes.</p> <p>They seek to please sight, smell and touch. They prefer complex and schematic figures.</p> <p>In their most primitive form they are a good eaters and enjoy taking the sun; the more sophisticated prefer an atmosphere of friendship and art</p>	<p>Visual (Colors and forms), Scents and Textures.</p>	<p>Strongly characterized products flamboyant, Shifting, varied.</p> <p>Greater use of colours.</p>

Table 2. Sensorial features (to be included in the object) correlated to sensorial characteristics in extroverted personalities
Source: Bedolla (2002)

cations on what is happening or will happen; in this way the sounds are associated to determined ideas, sensations, emotional states, etc. (Alcalde, 1988).

Smells have a considerable influence on the emotional states, motivations, and health. This influence is explained mainly due to the process of perception of the sense of smell. Thus the sense of smell is strongly influenced by the limbic system (located in the brain) and the properties of the smells since there are active and relaxing scents (Van Toller, Dodd, 1988).

Guideline Integration

The integration of the guidelines was based, as mentioned earlier, on how human sensorial groups relate to the aesthetic qualities of a product. These relations should henceforth be used as tools that allow the designer to distinguish users' preferences together with aesthetic and functional features of the product. This should facilitate innovation in design and lead to the creation of sensitively designed objects. That is to say, it should help bring users closer to their natural preferences and needs. The following figure gives an example of the integrated guidelines (Figure 1) (Table 2).

Guideline Usage and Tests

The purpose of this study was to put into practice and test some of the guidelines. We chose the guidelines related to the personality tendencies (introversion and extroversion). The guidelines were tested using one product (computer mouse), focusing on one sense: the tactile. The main objective was to know if people who present introvert or extrovert tendencies of personality prefer the product (mouse) redesigned based on the guidelines conceived. The evaluation was carried out by presenting three different models and control samples to 55 different users.

Figure 1. Sensorial attributes correlated to extroverted personalities

The Process of Sensorial Redesigning of the Mouse

The mouse was chosen as the experimental object because it is used daily by the participants chosen to test the product. Only one kind of sensorial attribute was taken into consideration for the re-designing process: tactility (form, size, and texture), so as to simplify the test and because touch is a form of direct experience useful for product evaluation. We used the touch information during product evaluation, the hand is the principal source of input to the touch perceptual system, and therefore the hand was proposed as the organ of touch called a person's outer brain.

Some of the main physical and emotional sensorial requirements considered that belong to people who tend to possess a predominant extrovert personality include: the application of sensorial attributes for a hard, vigorously sensorial stimulation, and the need of more energy to appreciate the stimulation of the senses. Extroverts present a major sensibility and preference for visual stimulation, especially to attributes such as colors and complex forms.

In contrast, people that possess a predominant introverted personality tend to reject and dislike strong sensorial stimulation. They need small quantities of energy to appreciate stimulation. They present major sensibility and preferences for tactile stimulation rather than other senses.

In the following table (table 3) we are describing the sensorial attributes of touch used for each group shown in the personality guidelines:

Figure 2. Mouse labeled A, designed with the guidelines for female gender, ages ranged from 18 to 45, and extroverted personalities: organic form, medium size, and with a slightly rugged texture.

SENSORIAL ATTRIBUTES OF TOUCH USED FOR EACH GROUP SHOWN IN THE PERSONALITY GUIDELINES		
Touch Attributes Used for the Extroverted Personality		
Form Shapes and asymmetric characteristics give rise to dynamic sensations for added energy to appreciate stimulation: organic, irregular, undefined shapes, decentralized elements, elongated, shifted.	Textures The idea of being entertained and playful is expressed through textures made up of an infinite number of small, dynamic, and heterogeneous structures.	Weight Lightness because it is lively, active, agile and dynamic. The concept is represented plastically by small or medium sized objects
Touch Attributes Used for the Introverted Personality		
Form Small, compact, refined, round, organic, harmonious proportions with rhythmic contours.	Textures Adaptable and flexible. They must be smooth with homogenous surfaces and convey warmth (for example furry objects) and convey moderate freshness (slight ruggedness or granularity).	Weight A little heavy, because that transmits an idea of durable goods. A large, thick, medium, or large sized object represents the concept plastically.

Table 3. Sensorial attributes of touch Used for each group showed in the personality guidelines

Four computer mouse were designed and labeled as A, B, C and D:

- Two mouse labeled as A were designed. The first one was designed using the guideline for extrovert personalities, and the second one using the guideline for introvert personalities. The goal of this study was, (already mentioned) to put into practice and test some of the guidelines.

The particular attributes of the mouse designed, were selected from the guidelines for extroverted personalities: organic form, medium size, and with a slightly rugged texture (Figure 2). Because the touch attributes were the ones to be evaluated a neutral color was used.

The specific sensorial characteristics used for the mouse designed with the guidelines for introvert personalities were: geometric and symmetric form, smooth texture and medium

size. Because the touch attributes were the ones to be evaluated, a neutral color was used (Figure 3).

- Mouse B was randomly modified ignoring the guidelines. The sensorial characteristics used were: blunt edges on the lower part, plain surface, and medium size. Because the touch attributes were going to be evaluated, a neutral color was used.
- Mouse C was randomly modified ignoring the guidelines. The sensorial characteristics used were: slight organic curves, with a texture that emphasizes the curves, and a small size. Because the touch attributes were going to be evaluated, a neutral color was used.
- Finally, an ordinary white mouse was labeled as D.

Figure 3. Mouse labeled A designed with the guidelines for female gender, ages ranged from 18 to 45, and introvert personalities: geometric and symmetric form, smooth texture and medium size. Because the touch attributes were the ones to be evaluated, a neutral color was used

Method

The method for eliciting the sensorial information from the user is known as the selection method, or the pluralist or relativist approach. The users interact with the object and describe their preferences.

Participants included a sample of 55 users, whose ages ranged from 18 to 45, from the Mixtec Technological University, Oaxaca, Mexico. Participants included students, administrative staff, and academics from the University.

Results

In the following tables (tables 4, 5) we are describing the results of the test to know if people who present introvert or extrovert tendencies of personality prefer the product (mouse) redesigned based on the guidelines conceived for them.

RESULTS OF THE TEST	
Redesigned mouse through the introvert personality guideline	
<p align="center">User preference reaction to the redesigned mouse Out of the 28 users identified with introverted personalities: 18 preferred the guideline redesigned mouse A, 2 preferred the randomly modified mouse B, 5 preferred the randomly modified mouse C, 3 preferred the ordinary mouse D</p>	
Mouse preferred by users identified with introverted personality	Order of importance of the qualities of the redesigned mouse that were preferred by users
Mouse A	Out of the 28 users 18 users preferred mouse A: 6 preferred it because of the form, 9 users preferred it because of the texture, 3 users preferred it because of the size
Mouse B	2 users preferred mouse B because of the texture
Mouse C	5 users identified with introvert personalities preferred mouse C: 3 preferred it because of the texture, 2 preferred it because of the form

Table 4. Results of the test for redesigned mouse through the introvert personality guideline

RESULTS OF THE TEST	
Redesigned mouse through the extrovert personality guideline	
<p align="center">User preference reaction to the redesigned mouse Out of the 27 users identified with an extrovert personality: 9 preferred the guideline-redesigned mouse A, 14 preferred the randomly modified mouse B, 1 preferred the randomly modified mouse C, 3 preferred the mouse D</p>	
Mouse preferred by users identified with an extrovert personality	Order of importance of the qualities of the redesigned mouse that were preferred by users
Mouse A	Out of 9 extroverts who preferred mouse A, 6 preferred it because of the form, 3 preferred it because of the size
Mouse B	Out of the 14 users identified with extrovert personality who preferred mouse B, 13 preferred it because of the form, 1 preferred it because of the size
Mouse C	The person who preferred mouse C preferred it because of the form
Mouse D	3 users preferred mouse D because of the form

Table 5. Results of the test for redesigned mouse through the extrovert personality guideline

Methodology for the Analysis of the Results

The social network analysis (Freeman, 2004) is a powerful tool that enables scientists to recognize certain behaviours and group patterns related to different social structures. It studies the relationships of actors (individuals or groups) in many different contexts. Information can be elicited from both individuals (micro level) and groups (macro level). Moreover, the method uses a resource known as “graph theory” that runs software analysis tools named Pajek. This allows a mathematical analysis of the relations between individuals and organizations in many different fields of knowledge. It is a powerful 32-bit program designed for a Windows operating system and used for the analysis of large networks.

Figure 4 gives the results of the test. It shows the mathematical model (network) that resulted from introducing our variables.

In figure 4 there is a net composed of 63 nodes. 55 of these nodes have an elliptical form. These represent the volunteers divided into two categories: introverted and extroverted. There are four triangular shapes, which represent the mice, and four rectangles, which represent the preferred qualities. The grade that each volunteer gave to each of the sensorial features was taken as the value that relates the user and each characteristic. Moreover, the relation between each volunteer and their preferred mouse was given the value of one.

When considering the value of these relations as a form of differentiation, Pajek allows us to see the rate of influence

each feature has on the participants. As the system takes into account the value of every relation in order to determine its position, those qualities that were graded similarly can be seen in the central part of the net (such as the form of the mouse). Size, for example, can be located closer to the nodes that represent the volunteers that preferred mouse A than to those that preferred another mouse. This means that this second quality was preferred. Likewise, it may be observed that form and size are more important than texture to those who choose mouse B.

Discussion

For the users identified with introverted personalities it can be seen that the guideline-redesigned mouse was preferred to the other three models, therefore, for this group of users, the introverted personality guideline was allowed to know the group of touch attributes (form, size and texture), which are capable of leading the product preferences. The quality preferred for them was texture (touch attribute).

However, as was observed, the tactile evaluation changed the preferences of the extroverted personalities towards mouse B. The quality preferred was form. Upon considering the preference of visual stimulation among other senses for this group, the quality preferred by them was visual and touch attributes. Thus we can infer that it is a strong influence of the visual sense and may be the cause of mouse B being preferred by extroverted users, rather than mouse A.

Based on this result, we can suppose that for our test, that

Figure 4. This network or mathematical model shows the preferences of 55 users concerning 4 specially designed mice (shown in nodes with the text mouse A, B, C or D). The users have been characterized as introverted or extroverted. In the centre the grade or level in which each sensorial attribute reflected in the mice generated particular preferences may be seen.

touch attributes had enough influence to lead product preference of the introvert user group. Moreover we can confirm that this group of users has preference for tactile stimulation (among other senses) because they preferred texture, which is a tactile attribute.

It is considered necessary to undertake more studies to re-evaluate and validate the relevance of touch attributes presented in the guideline for extrovert personality. We recommend incorporating visual attributes in the redesign, taking advantage of the correspondence between sensations derived from the human multisensory perception named synaesthesia, since it exists, as an innate human nature, a visual and tactile sensation complementation or correspondence. The quality preferred by the introvert user group was texture. This preference revealed its inclination towards tactile stimulation, rather than other senses. The second quality preferred was size, and the least preferred quality by this group was form.

For the extrovert user group, who preferred visual stimulation, the first quality preferred by them was form, due to its simultaneous visual and tactile nature. This preference for visual stimulation among other senses reveals for them the quality or attribute preferred in the mouse evaluation was form, due to its major visual components. Second quality preferred was size, at least texture (touch quality).

CONCLUSIONS

Upon considering previous studies and the proposals of several authors, the innovation of the “multisensory guidelines for design” permits to identify definite requirements, characteristics, and preferences of the people, which lead us to make out different sensorial groups of users. Moreover, the multisensory guidelines for design translate these specific human sensorial requirements, characteristics, and preferences into concrete multisensory qualities or attributes of design, which can be expressed through the five senses in the product design for definite groups of users.

The first test of some of the guidelines (personality tendencies) presented in this paper show that the personality characteristics are related to the preferences of the product designed.

Further tests are also required in order to continue and complete the evaluation of the guidelines and validate them.

This research found evidence that the specific or precise sensorial characteristics, capacities and requirements affect the preference of a product. The guidelines should represent an instrument (a complementary projection tool) to provide some criteria in applying the sensorial attributes of products. The sensorial and aesthetic product attributes can be used in a logical and appropriate way to correspond to the sensorial necessities and characteristics of a specific user group.

This new framework improves the possibility of recognizing

human preferences and the needs of specific groups of users. From the manufacturer's point of view, the application of this method should enable him/her to diversify models and specialize in particular sectors of society.

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HOW DEEP IS DEEP? A FOUR-LAYER MODEL OF INSIGHTS INTO HUMAN NEEDS FOR DESIGN INNOVATION

Mieke van der Bijl Brouwer

Design Innovation Research Centre, University of Technology, Sydney

✉ mieke.vanderbijl-brouwer@uts.edu.au

Kees Dorst

Design Innovation Research Centre, University of Technology, Sydney & Department of Industrial Design, Eindhoven University of Technology

✉ kees.dorst@uts.edu.au

ABSTRACT

It is generally acknowledged that knowledge about the people that are affected by a design proposal, supports successful design and innovation processes. In this paper we explore the question: what needs to be known about involved people to be able to innovate through design? Based on a literature analysis of human-centred design we propose a model with four levels of human insights: 1) the desired solutions; 2) the desired scenarios; 3) which goal drives this need; and 4) which human value or theme underlies these goals. We argue that radical innovation — which involves a reframe of the problem — can be supported by an investigation of the deepest level of this human insights framework: the thematic level. We show how themes are explored through a hermeneutic phenomenological exercise. This approach is illustrated with a design case in the context of social housing.

KEYWORDS: *human values, themes, design method, frame creation, social design*

INTRODUCTION

Ever since the publication of Henry Dreyfuss' 'Designing for people' (1955) there has been a general consensus in the design field that it is important that products meet the needs of the people that buy and use them. Insights into these needs are therefore an essential ingredient in designing products with a competitive advantage. Whilst Dreyfuss just focussed on gathering insights into ergonomic needs of people, later designers and design researchers have argued that products and services need to be accommodated as well to needs related to emotion and pleasure (P.M.A. Desmet & Hekkert, 2007; Jordan, 1999; Norman, 2002), and social needs (Forlizzi, 2008; Papanek, 1984).

To apply 'design thinking' in the broader field of innovation, Brown argued that in order to be able to innovate 'we need to put human beings to the center of the story. We need to learn to put people first' (Brown, 2009, p.39). Similarly, Bucolo et al. (2012) showed how design-led innovation is based on gathering 'deep customer insights'.

The inability of consumers, customers, and users to express what their true needs are makes designing for people a challenging activity. How to innovate through design, and how to find the 'latent needs' of consumers, are therefore ever-

popular topics for research in the design and innovation field. Norman and Verganti (2014) recently argued that human-centred or user-centred design could never lead to radical innovations. Contrary to this argument, Hekkert and van Dijk (2011) stated in their book 'Vision in design – a guidebook for innovators', that understanding people, their goals and concerns, their aspirations and motives, and the world surrounding them, indeed supports innovation. Similarly Sanders and Stappers (2012) argued that it is possible to innovate in human-centred ways, in their case through generative design, which allows people to express their needs and values.

In this paper we will contribute to this field of 'human-centred innovation' through proposing a model of levels of insights into human needs for innovation. Based on previous studies on design expertise (Dorst, 2013) we will show how an analysis of the deepest level of this model — the thematic level — supports design innovation. Thematic analysis questions the nature of certain human experiences through interrogating it from the 'heart of our existence' (van Manen, 1990), and is thus an in-depth approach to analysing human needs for design and innovation purposes. We will illustrate how thematic analysis works by applying it to a design case related to social housing.

HUMAN NEEDS AND DESIGN INNOVATION

Our research question is: ‘what do designers need to know about people’s needs to be able to innovate through design?’ According to Verganti (2008) design innovation is about the creation of new product meaning: the emotional and symbolic content of products. One of the more interesting practices of design that can be adopted in innovation processes for this purpose, is (re)framing the design problem (Dorst, 2011). In this paper we will focus on how insights into people’s needs support this framing process.

To explore this research question we will compare two models of design based on insights into human needs. From the business field we consider Sinek’s ‘what to why’ model (2009), and from the design field we consider Hekkert and van Dijk’s ViP model (2011).

Although Sinek’s immensely popular Ted talk ‘How great leaders inspire action’ (2009) is not directly about how customer insights can steer innovation, it does provide a simple model of different ways to look at customer needs. His mantra is ‘people don’t buy *what* you do, they buy *why* you do it’, which he explains in a three-layer circular model, with ‘what’ on the outside, ‘how’ in the middle, and ‘why’ at the inside. To be successful, he argues, you need to communicate from the inside out. As an example of a company who did not succeed in communicating from the inside out he refers to TiVo. Their ‘what’ was the product they provided: the TV set-top-box TiVo. The ‘how’ of this product was: pauses TV, skips commercials, rewinds live TV, and memorizes your viewing habit. According to Sinek TiVo failed commercially because they did not communicate the ‘why’ of this product: ‘to have total control over every aspect of your life’. Although Sinek remains ambivalent about how to arrive at the customer’s why — in other words how to innovate —, he shows in a simple way that it is important to focus on the ‘why’ or ‘raison d’être’ of a product.

This corresponds to Hekkert and van Dijk’s (2011) vision that design and innovation include ‘a shift away from thinking about “what” to thinking about “why” instead. With their Vision in Design (ViP) model and related design method they provide sound support for designers and innovators to create new product meaning. The ViP model consists of a ‘product level’, an ‘interaction level’ and a ‘context level’, which loosely corresponds respectively to Sinek’s what, how, and why level. The product level contains ‘the world of things’: products and their static characteristics such as colour, material, and dimensions. The interaction level is about the interaction between people and the product. Hekkert and van Dijk particularly advise designers to look at how the interaction *quality* can be characterised. The context level is about the worldview of the designer and includes people’s needs and motives.

The main idea of the ViP methodology is that in order to innovate, a designer first needs to design a set of views and considerations upon which the desired interaction and con-

sequently the product can be designed. This *vision* can be created by first ‘deconstructing’ existing products and trying to understand their reason of existence, and subsequently re-designing this vision by analysing trends and developments that are changing people’s needs and motives. They illustrate this with an analysis of the context of ‘parenting’ for the design of a baby stroller. In the 1990s, considerations underlying the design of baby strollers were that ‘people want things to be cheap’, ‘people want to move their kids’, and ‘people want ease of use’. The designer of the Bugaboo, Max Barenburg, saw how this context had changed with both parents working and having less and less time to spend with their kids. The new context was ‘they want the best for their kids’ and ‘flexibility in moving in the urban jungle’, which resulted in the design of Bugaboo: a stroller that creates a comfortable space for the child, protects the child to the utmost, and provides the parents with a luxurious mobility aid (Hekkert & van Dijk, 2011, p.136). By reframing the problem as seeing it as a problem of ‘efficient transportation’ to a problem of ‘wanting the best for the kids’ this designer managed to design a very successful product.

The ViP model and Sinek’s model lead us to the conclusion that insights into human needs can be gathered on a product or what level — what do people need; an interaction or how level — how do people want to interact with what they need; and a why level — why do people want to interact in that way. For the remainder of this paper we will focus on the why level.

To build a model of human needs insights for innovation we look a bit closer at the ‘context level’ of the ViP model. This level is the complete set of starting points — and their mutual relationships — selected by the designer for a given design task (Hekkert & van Dijk, 2011, p.231). Human needs can be found within the ‘principles’ and ‘trends’ on this context level. Principles are factors that are by their unvarying nature, constant over longer periods of time. The term refers to immutable laws or general patterns that can be found in human beings or nature. Trends are more dynamic factors, concerning tendencies in behaviour, values, or preferences of (groups of) people (ibid., p.233). Trends can be based on principles, e.g. the trend ‘to send hundreds of text messages per week’ is based on the principle that ‘youngsters want to belong to a group’. They are both needs, but on different levels. The trend in this case is how the principle plays out in a certain context.

To further refine this model we refer to the recent work of the second author of this paper (Dorst, 2013) on how the reframing of problems or ‘frame creation’ can be supported by an analysis of *themes*. Frame creation is the ability of expert designers to create new approaches to problems. A combination of empirical studies into expert designer’s practices, fundamental analysis into reasoning patterns, and different forms of rationality, and experimental practice, have led to the development of a frame creation process model (Dorst, 2011). An in-depth explanation of this model is outside the scope of this paper. We focus on those parts of the model that connect insights into human needs to the creation of frames and thus support innovation. This part roughly consists of

three steps: In the ‘context’ and ‘field’ steps, the needs of the direct and more broader stakeholders in the original design problem are investigated. This step is about analysing what is important to those people and organisations. The next step includes the identification of the common themes that can be found within this context and field. This is similar to identifying the ‘whys’. Then the model proposes to go even deeper by a thorough analysis of these themes through hermeneutic phenomenology (van Manen, 1990). The patterns that can be found in the themes through this analysis can then be used to create frames.

Before explaining how such a thematic analysis works we first explain what is meant by ‘themes’ and how it relates to the ViP model. Phenomenological themes may be understood as the structures of experience. So when we analyse a phenomenon, we are trying to determine what the themes are, the experiential structures that make up that experience (van Manen, 1990, p.79). We could thus first look at (desired) experiences of stakeholders on the ‘how level’ and then try to find the ‘structures’ that underlie these experiences on the ‘why’ level. Themes described in phenomenology are typically both deeply personal and universal among humanity (Dorst, 2013). There is a similarity between the themes described by van Manen and the principles in the context level described for the ViP model. Since both authors take the phenomenon ‘parenting’ as an example it is possible to compare the two.

For example, when van Manen (1990) explores the phenomenon ‘parenting’, he identifies themes such as ‘preparing the child’s world as a place to be and to become’ and ‘exercising parental responsibility’ (ibid., p.168). Hekkert and van Dijk (2011, p.146) mention as relevant principles in the future con-

text of parenting amongst others ‘the notion of being responsible all of the time’, and ‘parenthood puts strong pressure on the ability to regulate emotions’. These principles are clearly on a comparable level of human needs as themes. The themes/principles can be analysed independently of the context, the baby stroller. The other type of context factors as described by Hekkert & van Dijk contrarily are context dependent needs and indicate how these principles play out; e.g., the trend ‘baby strollers are more and more an expression of identity’ is grounded in the theme ‘identity’. Since trends and themes both would be part of the ‘why’ level, but have different influences on the design innovation process, we propose to split up the why level in a level of ‘goals’ (trends) and ‘themes’.

A model of insights into human needs for design innovation

Based on the above analysis we distinguish four levels when trying to understand human needs for innovation. These levels are illustrated in Figure 1, and are shortly explained by means of a design case in which a student design team designed a carrier bike: a bicycle with a box in the front which in the Netherlands is mostly used to transport children (van der Bijl-Brouwer & van der Voort, 2013a). Although the students did not use our proposed model in their design process, the resulting design illustrates how human needs on the different levels explain the design.

We refer to the top-level as the ‘solutions’ level, including solutions and their characteristics, be it physical product solutions, services, policies etc. For the carrier bike the team found that parents wanted a detachable rain hood.

Figure 1: a model of insights into human needs for design & Innovation

Figure 2: a carrier bike to ‘explore the world together’

The level below is the ‘scenarios’ level. It includes all needs that are related to how people want to interact and experience certain solutions in specific situations. Parents wanted the hood to be easy to set up in case of sudden weather changes during cycling.

The goal level describes why people want certain scenarios to occur in the context of the solution space. In the carrier bike case parents wanted to always protect their children from wind and rain while being seated in the box.

At the base of the model the ‘themes’ level explains what the origin is of certain goals. In this case the underlying phenomenon again is ‘parenting’. The theme that underlies the goal ‘protecting children from wind and rain’ is grounded in the theme ‘protection’. This student team managed to reframe their design problem by further investigating parent needs. Parents had indicated that they enjoyed the carrier bike because they could see their children in front of them, and it was nice to be able to talk to them. The team furthermore found in literature about the emotional development of children that it was important for them to ‘explore the world’ around them. They then reframed their problem from a ‘transport and protect’ problem to a problem of ‘exploring the world together’. This frame can be explained through the theme of guidance as a parent. Guidance is part of ‘pedagogic competence’, an essential theme of parenting. Parents need to be able to help the child grow up and give shape to life (van Manen, 1990). Guidance means that an interaction between the guide (parent) and the guided person (the child) takes place while the guided person interacts with the world. The interaction in the case of the carrier bike means that it should always be possible for the parents to talk to and see the child, in order to be able to point the child at interesting elements of the environment, to give feedback on the child’s observations, and to see the child’s reaction. The interaction of the child with the world means that the child should always be able to look around and observe the world whilst seated in the box. The solution the student team created was a transparent hood

that is open on the parent’s side, so it always allows this guidance to take place, even in different weather conditions (Figure 2). This example shows how the themes related to ‘parenting’ form the basis of a reframe of the problem.

HUMAN-CENTRED DESIGN METHODOLOGY

The above example shows how it is retrospectively possible to rationalize how insights into deeper levels of human needs can support an innovative design process. Of course post-rationalization is easier than actually going through this design process. Likewise it is easy to see how a good vision as proposed by Hekkert and van Dijk (2011) can steer successful design, but creating this vision is not an easy task. It is a design skill that needs practice and experience to be developed.

We contribute to this work by providing additional tools for innovation through the reframing of problems in design situations of social design, which involve decision-makers that are often not designers themselves. In the next session we first give a short overview of different available methods to gather insights into human needs before presenting a hermeneutic phenomenological method to analyse the needs on the deepest level.

Methods for gathering insights into human needs for design

For every level of human needs, different methods are available to gather insights into these needs. Insights on the ‘what’ level are mostly gathered by market research techniques. In design these types of insights are mostly useful for benchmarking purposes and not for design innovation. To get insight into *how* people experience or want to experience a certain solution, various techniques are available that measure different aspects of experiences such as: (self-) reports of experiences and emotions (for example PrEmo, Desmet, 2005); scenario analysis (for example (van der Bijl - Brouwer & van

der Voort, 2013b); interaction qualities (Hekkert & van Dijk, 2011); user testing (for example, Sharp et al., 2007) etc. To gather insights into people's goals one can use techniques such as interviews, as in persona investigation techniques (Pruitt & Grudin, 2003). To identify human values and meanings comparable to themes one can use techniques such as generative tools (Sanders & Stappers, 2012), to glean them from users themselves, or techniques such as ViP (Hekkert & van Dijk, 2011), to define them as a designer. In this paper we don't want to focus on how one gathers insights on the thematic level, but more on what is done with these insights to make them useful in a design innovation or reframing process.

As mentioned above, the work of the second author (Dorst, 2013) has shown how an analysis of themes through hermeneutic phenomenology can support reframing of a problem and consequently innovation. The frame creation process of which this thematic analysis is part has been successfully applied in numerous social design projects in the area of crime prevention (for example, Lulham et al., 2012). In this paper we will show how such a thematic analysis can be executed with involved decision-makers in a practical example.

Using hermeneutic phenomenology to analyse the deepest level of human needs

Hermeneutic phenomenology is a method to identify and analyse themes (van Manen, 1990). It is a means to research the meaning of 'lived experience'. The phenomenological orientation of this method means that it fundamentally differs from positivistic orientations towards experiences and emotions. Phenomenology does not allow for empirical generalizations, the production of law-like statements, or the establishment of functional relationships. Instead phenomenological research finds its point of departure in the *situation*, which for purpose of analysis, description, and interpretation functions as an exemplary nodal point of meanings that are embedded in the situation (van Manen, 1990, p.18).

The way we have experimented with hermeneutic phenomenology is by applying it in workshop sessions of social design teams, based on previous case studies (Dorst, 2013), and inspired by the guidelines for thematic analysis provided by Rijken (2013). First, themes are identified by searching for common patterns in analysed needs on the how and goal level of involved stakeholders. These needs are gathered through various research methods prior to the workshop (see for a comparable example, Tomkin & Watson, 2013). We then proceed to further analyse these themes by investigating their meaning and relationships. A core element of the method is to explore the relations by sharing personal experiences related to a theme. For example, Rijken (2013) explains how to investigate the theme 'fear' through asking people: have you ever experienced fear? What triggered it? What did it feel like? What were you thinking? What changed it? What did you do? Did others play a role? By having different team members share these experiences in an iterative process a pattern can emerge that shows the structure of a theme. For example, fear is related in a structured way to insecurity, risks, con-

fidence, uncertainty etc. Other ways to explore themes are consulting scientific literature and philosophy on specific themes; and gathering artworks that express a theme (Rijken, 2013). The universality of the themes makes it possible to analyse them independently of customers or end-users, and independent of the problem context. To move from the themes to reframe the problem, it is useful to look at how the elements of the theme are dealt with in domains outside the problem context (Dorst, 2013). Through using metaphors, a frame can then be created which forms a bridge between problems and solutions. Different frames should then be analysed on their 'fruitfulness' i.e. the extent to which they open up the solution space. In the next section we will illustrate this process with a social design case study.

A CASE STUDY OF THEMATIC ANALYSIS IN SOCIAL DESIGN

Slowly but surely it is becoming clear that design is an essential element of dealing with complex social problems (Brown, 2009; Dorst, 2013). Applying human-centred innovation to social problems is difficult, with solutions that do not just include products and services but also new policies and programs. The fact that social problems consist of multiple related and interacting stakeholders makes them complex to deal with (Forlizzi, 2008). Moreover, the team that takes decisions for social design will most likely consist of people who might not be used to working in a designerly way, such as public servants, NGO's, and in some cases members of the community. Innovating for such problems is therefore an even more challenging activity. We will show how such social problems can be approached through aforementioned analysis of themes, by showing its application in the redesign of a social housing service.

Context of the case

The case we will describe here is a workshop session with a group of senior public servants from different Australian state government departments. The workshop was organized as part of a training program in innovation. In different sessions the public servants learned about innovation methods through applying each method briefly to a case related to problems in social housing. We offered a workshop in 'frame creation', which included a thematic analysis. Since the workshop was a training session, and not an actual design session, the group had gathered fewer insights into human needs on the scenario and goal level than we would generally recommend. However, our own expertise and wide experience in working with public housing organisations provided enough input for the workshop to go through a thematic analysis session. Consequently we found this case appropriate to study the process of thematic analysis in the context of a social design problem. The group consisted of sixteen participants who were subdivided into four teams. Each team went through a frame creation process facilitated by an expert, including the authors of this paper.

Figure 3: insights into human needs for the social housing case study on the four levels for the original frame and one alternative frame

Preparation of the thematic analysis

The original brief for the problem drew on an historical framing of ‘mutual obligation’ between the provider of social housing and the tenants (see for example, Kinnear, 2002). The aim of social housing is to provide temporary housing for tenants until they can move on to more independent types of living. The obligation of tenants is to improve their own life circumstances through, for example, education and employment, so that they will be able to ‘move on’. Since there are too many tenants that do not fulfil this obligation, social housing is currently reaching its capacity. Mutual obligation is based on social contract theory, the presumption that individuals consciously decide to enter into political society, agreeing to sacrifice certain liberties in return for the State’s protection (ibid., goal level in figure 3). When we discussed this frame with the group there was a consensus that it did not help them come up with ideas on how to address the issue. It did not help them in finding a ‘path to action’ (Dorst, 2013, p.7.).

To situate this problem we first showed three short online movies about communities in areas where a large proportion of the population lives in social housing. The movies show how families, single parents, teenagers and volunteers try to better their living circumstances, particularly those of children, and provide a glimpse of how people live in social housing. This is a simple form of research on the scenario level of our framework.

We then investigated which stakeholders are involved in the sketched problem (the context) and which stakeholders could potentially be involved in future solutions (the field). They include housing and residents (families, pensioners, long term, short term, people with disabilities, youth, single parents), NGO’s, ethnic groups, schools, churches, police,

transport services, job network providers, vocational educational institutions, health services etc. We then looked at what was important to them (the goal level) to try and find shared themes.

Thematic analysis

Common themes that were found in the context and field included (across the different teams): self-determination and autonomy, control, belonging, trust, shelter and stability.

Figure 4: thematic analysis of control and autonomy (blue sticky notes)

Through a hermeneutic phenomenological exercise as explained above, some of the themes were unpacked. As an example, we summarize the analysis for ‘control’ here.

Control and autonomy are themes that apply to all the involved stakeholders. We shared personal experiences of when you feel (or do not feel) in control of your own decisions and what it feels like, and when you relinquish control to someone else. To be in control (autonomy) means having options available and knowing what the options are, and to be authorized to make the decisions. Feeling that you are in control leads to a sense of calm and self-respect. However, taking control can also mean that you need to step outside your comfort zone and it therefore requires confidence in one’s capacities. People are willing to give control away to someone they trust and when they have the freedom to choose who to trust, for example in the case of giving control to the pilot of a plane, or to a doctor when having to go into surgery. When you are empowered to be in control of decisions that affect others, it leads to a sense of being respected. Figure 4 shows the results of the thematic analysis as explored during the workshop on a flip chart.

Reframing

The thematic analysis showed how control and autonomy are related to other themes such as trust, empowerment, safety and confidence. We then looked for metaphors that embody similar patterns of relationships to explore frames. Here we show two examples related to the theme ‘control’ that illustrate how the thematic analysis can change the perspective on the problem.

Scaffolding: this frame uses the metaphor ‘scaffolding in education’ as a perspective on the problem. Scaffolding consists essentially of the adult ‘controlling’ those elements of the task that are initially beyond the learner’s capacity, thus permitting him to concentrate upon and complete only those elements that are within his range of competence (Wood et al., 1976). Once a student masters a task, the scaffolding can be removed and the student will then be able to complete the task again on his own. This frame made participants realize that what social housing does now is to take over control by imposing rules (mutual obligation). They do not remove the scaffold, so it’s a step back.

Reconnect/ (family) reunion (Figure 3): this frame is based on allowing people to give control to people they have chosen to trust. The frame is about bringing people together and having them find a common background that connects them. This in turn supports building a social network. The social housing organisation in this frame does not provide the assistance itself, but organizes events in the community that brings people together so they can help each other. A common background could be a shared cultural history, shared interests (sports, crafts), or common circumstances (single parent). A similar frame found in another team was that of community sports clubs to help build a sense of community.

Next steps

The frames of ‘reunion’ and ‘scaffolding’ are completely different perspectives on the problem than the original frame of ‘mutual obligation’. The scaffolding frame has an individual focus while the reunion frame has a clear communal focus. The frames could therefore potentially be complementary in providing paths to action. The next step in frame creation would be to further explore the fruitfulness of the frames with regard to creating solution directions (futures) and to investigate their feasibility (Dorst, 2013). For a complex case like this more research and workshop sessions would be needed to explore a broader variety of themes, frames, and futures. However, the case shows well how an analysis of the deepest level of human needs can support reframing the problem in a case of social design.

CONCLUSION

In this paper we explored the research question: ‘what do designers need to know about people’s needs to be able to innovate through design?’ We have formulated a preliminary answer to this question by proposing a fledgling model of levels of insights into human needs for innovation. We have shown in a case study how an analysis of the deepest level of this model, the thematic level, can support design innovation processes in a social design context. However, more case studies are needed to investigate which depth of insight is needed for which type of innovation, and which type of design problem and design context. This will be the focus of our future research.

As we mentioned in the introduction, Norman and Verganti (2014) argued that human-centred design could never lead to radical innovation. This is clearly true for traditional forms of human or user-centred design, which focus on iteratively designing products that fit user’s needs as expressed by these users themselves. However, if radical innovation is about the creation of new meaning, exploring this level of meaning on its deepest human level can indeed support such radical innovations. Users need not be involved directly in the design process in order to innovate, but human needs should be at the centre of the design process, in order to create new meaning.

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INTEGRAL DESIGN TUTORING MODEL AS A KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER STRATEGY FOR SMES IN COLOMBIA

Javier Ricardo Mejia Sarmiento
ID-StudioLab, Faculty of Industrial Design Engineering,
Delft University of Technology, Landbergstraat 15, NL-2628CE Delft, the Netherlands
Ministry of Commerce, Industry and Tourism of Colombia, Vice-Ministry of Business Development, Calle
28 No 13 A - 15 Bogotá, Colombia
✉ J.R.MejiaSarmiento@tudelft.nl

Jose Emilio Jimenez Ibañez
Polytechnic University of Valencia, School of Design Engineering, Camino de Vera, s/n 46022 Valencia
✉ emiliojimenez@fivelines.es

Daniela Chavarria Devia
University of Los Andes, Faculty of Design and Architecture, Cra 1 N° 18A- 12 Bogotá, Colombia
✉ danielachd19@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Colombia has been transformed into the third country with the best business environment in L.A.; however, investment in Research, Development and Innovation (RD&I) is only 0,2% of the GPD. Taking into account that 98% of the Colombian enterprises are SMEs, from which 5% invest only 2% of its annual budget in design, the National Industrial Design Program (MinCIT) saw the need to develop the Integral Design Tutoring Model.

The model makes a bet for empathy and emotional intimacy as tools to transfer the necessary knowledge so that the local businessperson develops an innovation culture based on design thinking.

To test the model, the Integral Design Tutoring Project was developed as a pilot. This four-months project allowed an interdisciplinary team, conducted by designers, to accompany twenty SMEs. Through a process developed in three stages it was possible to prove that, through empathy and emotional intimacy, one can achieve knowledge transfer to business people and their organizations in an effective, efficient and successful way. This knowledge transfer allows the organization to develop human centered design processes in a systematic, independent and autonomous way.

KEYWORDS: *Design knowledge transfer, empathy and emotional intimacy, tutoring, Contextual design approach and Colombian SMEs.*

INTRODUCTION

The Ministry of Commerce, Industry, and Tourism of Colombia (MinCIT, for its initials in Spanish: Ministerio de Comercio, Industria y Turismo), through the National Design Program (PNDI, for its initials in Spanish: Programa Nacional de Diseño Industrial) promotes design as an innovation driver for SMEs through the development of activities, projects, workshops, and by providing information in this field. The PNDI-MinCIT works in three strategic lines: knowledge transfer about design, viewing, and promoting successful design cases and public policies about design.

As part of the first strategic line, a novel approach named Integral Design Tutoring Model (MADI, for its initials in Spanish: Modelo de Acompañamiento en Diseño Integral) was developed. From this model a set of Integral Design Tutoring Projects for the world class SMEs in Colombia was proposed. These projects should be replicable and scalable, depending on regional and sectorial needs. The final objective of these projects is the transfer of knowledge and design thinking abilities to the Colombian SMEs that, according to recent studies, do not have enough instruction on the subject.

These projects expect to generate 'solutions spaces' as a response to branding problems and human centered innovation.

They use empathy and emotional intimacy within a tutoring process to transfer knowledge from the team to the enterprise in the most effective way possible.

This paper's central theme is the explanation of the MADI approach model, and works around concepts like empathy and design for social innovation as a conceptual framework. It refers specifically to the pilot project (PADI+2013), developed during 2013, in which twenty SMEs were intervened, fourteen located in Bogotá and six in Cartagena. The conclusions and recommendations are based on this project, its application and projections.

REFERENCE FRAME

Context, project definition and background

Through the National Development Plan 2010-2014 'Prosperity for All', the Colombian government defined a set of sustainable economic growth objectives that must be fulfilled based on three large pillars: innovation, policies on competitiveness and productivity, and stimulation of the growth and job-generation engines.

According to this plan 'Innovation becomes the optimum mechanism to guarantee long term sustainability of growth and competitiveness of the country'. Innovation consists in 'creating new ways of organizing, executing, producing, delivering, merchandising, selling, and relating clients and suppliers, while achieving the generation of added value throughout the production chain' (DNP, 2011, p.10).

Both to those who offer or demand design, it is clear that the process of innovation is closely linked to the design process and that both should be positioned in high levels in organizations. (Romero et al., 2009, p.151).

As part of the country's innovation system, design has been recognized at government level in 1994 and appears in the MinCIT portfolio. The Ministry, through the PNDI-MinCIT, promotes design in Colombian industry. The National Design System, defined by the Colombian Government, is coordinated and lead by the PNDI-MinCIT with the intention to promote design as an innovation driver for SMEs through the development of activities, projects, workshops, and information in this field. With this project, the Ministry contributes to discover scenarios and synergies to cooperate and work in the country's design supply and demand as an ecosystem that provides spaces to improve the companies' competitiveness, and to increase the quality level of products in the country while developing the design sector in the process.

According to the Colombian government, the country currently evidences considerable lagging compared to peers with similar characteristics in the development of science, technology, and innovation. The total investment in research and development in Colombia is 0.2% of GDP, which is a very low level, compared to countries such as Argentina, which invests 0.5%, Chile 0.7%, Brazil 0.8% or South Korea 3.2% (DNP, 2011, p.10).

Design is in a similar situation. 53% of the Colombian SMEs do not have budget for design activities and only 2% invest more than 5% of its budget in this activity. 'Resources destined to design and development activities in the majority of cases are not adequate and do not coincide with what was expressed by managers during the interview' (Bohorquez et al., 2008, p.3).

According to the Design Occupational Characterization in the Colombian Industry study (Bohorquez et al., 2008), the inclusion of design in the organization is still low and requires more stimuli from different vantage points.¹

'The transverse participation of design is an aspect that starts being acknowledged, valued and understood as a discipline that interacts with other components of the value chain' (Romero et al., 2009, p.155). Around 70% of enterprises express concerns for innovation (Bohorquez et al., 2008, p.82), but do not necessarily include design.

The above mentioned studies evidence that a central cause for the low insertion of design in the productive sector in the country is lack of knowledge or misconceptions, and partial knowledge of the role of design in the organization. Figure 1 contrasts the contact level SMEs have with design and the degree of elaboration they have on this knowledge. This contrast allows to describe the four forms in which a business owner can understand design intervention in the firm: 1) Not knowing anything about design, 2) believing design is styling, 3) considering design as a process or 4) Understanding design as innovation (Mejía, 2012). This knowledge scale contrasts with the size of the firm and the investment in design themes, it makes evident that micro enterprises do not have knowledge about design or have partial versions of its tasks (e.g. believing the designer is just the product configurator).

In the country, the role of the design businesses has been basically consulting: 'enterprise consulting can be seen as a professional service or as a method of practical consulting and helping [...] simultaneously, it is also a method to help firms in he betterment of the management and business practices, as well as in the collective and individual performance' (Kubr, 2002, p.4). Referring to this way of professional service 'some business people have perceived a lack of clarity in the portfolio services of the firms that offer design', they mention that, 'a supply based on very interesting terms or contents is

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1. According to this study, the insertion should be divided into three: Graphic industry, in which it is evident that the participation and acknowledgement that graphic design professionals have on most development and design activities. In the plastic sector, professional design insertion is practically zero, since development and design are usually in the hands of engineers, maybe because of the high percentage of technical work required. In the textile and garment sector, where design and development activities are not in hands of fashion designers, according to the managers, these professionals do not meet the requirements in terms of knowledge of the productive processes the firms have. All this added to the well known fact that there is a big group of these organizations that dedicate themselves to the maquila services and not to develop their own products, which could explain why these firms do not invest in designers.

Figure 1. Knowledge scales in design for the Colombian SME
 Source: National Design Program (PNDI-MinCIT), <http://www.mipymes.gov.co/publicaciones.php?id=935>

generated, but it is presented within a confusing publicity that tends to create expectations and curiosity but that sometimes produces disappointing results' (Romero et al., 2009, p.155).

These services do not have continuity and prevent business people from learning to value design 'the message, in this sense, is that the service supply language must be clear and should leave no room for confusions' (ibid., p.155), it must also guarantee that the business person sees design as a mechanism to innovate.

Additionally, 'it is perceived that the resources assigned to design are growing since their importance in the sustainability of organizations has been acknowledged' (ibid., p.155); that is why it is very important to cultivate skills and abilities that guarantee knowledge in this field and allow their use by the firms to augment their capacity in this form of innovation.

REFERENCES AND INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK

The MinCIT is the national executive ministry of the government of Colombia concerned with promoting economic growth through trade, tourism, and industrial growth. The Ministry,

through the PNDI-MinCIT, works in three strategic lines:² Knowledge Transfer about Design, Viewing and Promoting Successful Design Cases, and Public Policies and Strategic Plans.

This paper's central theme is the explanation of the Integral Design Tutoring Model MADi, and the Integral Design Tutoring Project (PADI+2013), developed during 2013 as part of the first strategic line posited previously — knowledge transfer about design.

This type of project has only one reference in the country, the ACUNAR project (Design transference program to productive communities for innovation and competitiveness), developed by the extension center of the Arts Faculty at National University of Colombia. This program's objective was to transfer design to productive communities from the product dimension. To do that, a participative design methodology was used (research, action, and participation), in this way, all organization areas were touched. The objective was to strengthen productive communities to make them more competitive, vis-a-vis the current market dynamics. The ACUNAR portfolio was con-

2. The PNDI-MinCIT works in three strategic lines: 1. KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER ABOUT DESIGN. This strategic line aims to transfer knowledge about design to SMEs.

stituted by the following services: Strengthening of productive networks, product development, and improvement, packing development and improvement, and work area improvement. The knowledge transference model was based on workshops on diverse themes (ACUNAR program, 2011).

The closest international referent to ACUNAR is the ADÑ Project, Spanish good practices; it is a knowledge transfer and direct intervention program in the area of design and innovation as tools to the creation of value, the improvement of competitiveness, and the SMEs' sustained economic growth.

Project approach

MADI is posited as a model to develop multiple types of action; some of them can be Integral Design Tutoring Models. These projects tutor Colombian SMEs of the world class sectors and posit contextualized solution spaces for branding problems and human centered innovation where, through empathy and emotional intimacy, an interdisciplinary team (the authors of the paper were part of this team), lead by designers, transfer knowledge and abilities in 'design thinking', necessary to the autonomous development of integral design projects, form a contextualized perspective for diverse problem levels for each SME; all adapted to the Colombian context.

1.1. DESIGN AND INNOVATION WORKSHOPS FOR BUSINESS COMPETITIVENESS (TD&ixCE). These workshops aim to develop diverse topics about design for the Colombian SMEs with the intention to motivate them to use it as a key approach and tool, inviting them to buy design and, finally, to do design made in Colombia.

1.2. MANUAL OF DESIGN AND INNOVATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMEs. This manual based its content on the key concept that defines design as a particular way to create innovation, and it enables a bridge to be built between users, thoughts on their needs, and the company creating business opportunities linked to the enterprise potentialities in order to grow in a sustainable way within the knowledge economy.

1.3. INTEGRAL DESIGN TUTORING PROJECT PADI+2013. The project was made to help 20 Colombian SMEs and four governmental projects in the New Product Development — NPD process to create a 'culture of design' in order to decrease the existing gap between professional designers and SMEs.

2. VIEWING AND PROMOTING SUCCESSFUL DESIGN CASES. This strategic line tries to build a set of case-studies about design related to the SMEs in the country.

2.1. DOCUMENTARY SERIES: Design case studies in Colombian SMEs. Success through design. This documentary promotes design as a crucial element in innovation, publicizing, and recognizing the professional role of design in Colombian industry with the presentation of design cases where design is key for the competitiveness of the company.

2.2. SAMPLE'S DESIGN IN COLOMBIA (application). The Sample's design is a digital publication that shows successful design cases, including product, graphic, digital, interior, and fashion design, in order to illustrate New Product Development NPD processes in the Colombian SMEs. The main goal is to visualize the final results of design in the national industry.

3. PUBLIC POLICIES AND STRATEGIC PLAN. The last but not least strategic line is responsible for planning and programming all strategic actions regarding the PNDI-MinCIT until a public policy is developed.

Integral Design Tutoring Model Definition (MADI)

MADI's general approach is made from a philosophic perspective that has three fundamental axes: Epistemological, from which the model is understood as a conceptual system that can be applied to a specific context; praxeological, from the integration of a series of methodologies close to design thinking and close to empathic tutoring; and phenomenological, how processes and results can be reached in the applied development of MADI to specific projects.

This way of tackling the model constitutes a bid to understand knowledge as a cyclic and iterative flow that, through empathic accompaniment, gets transferred during the project and where, thanks to the emotional intimacy³ generated during the process, creates knowledge for enterprises, designers and institutions.

To posit an intervention model, the work team developed a conceptual framework aligned with the chosen perspective to allow the selection of actors, the method, and the process. The first concept in this framework is 'user centered design', defined by the PNDI-MinCIT, as the differentiating element of design facing other innovation disciplines. This value allows the business person to understand users as human beings with needs, expectations, and hopes; this is very useful for Colombian SMEs that historically have not visualized their consumers in any way. For the project, users are conceived as the origin and destination of products, services, and organizations' experiences.

It is understood that the concept 'branding problem integral solution' is not a corporate image problem (logo, logo symbol, etc.), but a development of a narrative axis capable of aligning the strategic, tactic, and operational axes of an organization acting as an integrating nucleus and helping construct a branding experience.

Within the model, there are three actors (National Design System, 2009), an interdisciplinary team, lead by designers, responsible for the planning and rendering of the project, the tutoring, both to enterprises and institutions, and to develop the conceptual framework, and determine the perspective for the construction and execution of the knowledge transfer. The team works from the premise that the implementation of design thinking can produce in enterprises a better understanding of the users and, thus, a development of their abilities for competitiveness and innovation.

It is understood that it is necessary for the presence of government and non-government institutions to support and manage the logistics of the project, facilitating the management of resources, selecting the SMEs and working as a platform for project development. Besides, there is a tutoring process in logistics and financing themes.

3. The PADI work team understands the concept of emotional intimacy as how they established empathic relationships with the SMEs. By using specific tools they promote business person's awareness of the problem situation and understanding their enterprises within a context that was centered in its users.

Figure 2. MADI's General scheme.

The central actors of MADI are enterprises and users that, according to the model, can be of any kind, size, and productive sector, including social or community based organizations. These organizations will be tutored within a conceptual framework (user centered design process and branding integral solution) from where they will receive knowledge transfer on design thinking.

MADI establishes a set of phases, inside a methodology, equivalent to any other enterprise design process like IDEO or Smart Design, which focuses on the importance of design thinking for the formulation of contextualized solutions.

The design process allows obtaining, analyzing, decanting, and prototyping the required information for the development of a design project.

These stages depend on the approach perspective with the actors; they should be tutored with specific tools that facilitate actions while advancing the project.

As final products to be delivered by any project based on MADI, and under the premise that it is a tutoring model and not a traditional consulting process, there is the need to help the business person construct a Contextualized Solutions Space — CSS — instead of finding a specific solution for the product,

the image, or the business. The CSS offers a set of conceptual answers intertwined within a scenario that allows the organization to make the decisions from within instead of the typical process with external consulting.

This CSS is posited from two different perspectives: a tool use and methodological perspective, and a knowledge transfer and its pedagogical components perspective.

Based on design thinking, from the methodological perspective, it is sought that the businessperson understands design as a systematized process supported by a set of tools that could help in the solutions of diverse problems, beyond being just a product configurator. This paradigm change is achieved when the CSSs are constructed based on human-centered context analysis, to develop efficient solutions aligned with the three axes: strategic, at the level of the business model; tactic, at the level of portfolio; and processes and operative, at the level of product, service, and brand identity or consumer experience.

Knowledge transfer, through the use of different tools, allows the construction of abilities based on design thinking that facilitates the understanding of problems and their solutions. This process, as a pedagogical bet, intends for the businessperson to be able to grow autonomously when the project is completed.

PRESENTATION OF THE INTEGRAL DESIGN TUTORING PROJECT PADI+2013

General presentation of the pilot PADI+2013 and used methodologies

Taking into account the definition of the model and the intention to prove and corroborate that, through the use on empathy and emotional intimacy, one can obtain better results in the design intervention; the PNDI-MinCIT saw the need to formulate a pilot tutoring project for some Colombian SMEs. To develop this project, and to align it will two national programs (Productive Transformation Program and Innpulsa Colombia), the PNDI-MinCIT was supported by a national operating institution (Confecámaras), and two regional institutions (Bogotá Chamber of Commerce and Cartagena Chamber of Commerce). This pilot was named Integral Design Tutoring Project PADI+2013.

PADI+2013 had an intensive duration of sixteen weeks when an interdisciplinary team, lead by designers, worked with twenty SMEs (eight micro, eight small and four middle sized), and four institutional projects (three national and one district-level). From these, fourteen SMEs were located in Bogotá and six in Cartagena.

In general terms, PADI+2013 was developed in three stages: **understanding**, **conceptualizing** and **delivering**. In each of these stages, specific methodologies were used to know fast and in depth the organizations functioning, their interaction with their users, and the context and business scenario in which they operate.

In this sense, the first thing to be analyzed was the SME; the diagnostic tools (as part of the understanding stage) allowed

to empathize with the organization and its members. The ethnographic tools helped understanding users and their interaction with the organization.

It is important to note that the general objective was to construct solution spaces and not direct solutions; so, it was necessary to analyze the present scenario (current context), and also to project a future scenario to open the vision of the organizations to innovative and lasting solutions.

Finally, in the last phase, each organization was given a set of improvements in the form of a business model, new or improved portfolios, and service or concept design for new products and spaces. It is understood that in each one of these phases, the team developed, on the side, a double way to exercise knowledge transfer.

Development of the PADI+2013 pilot

In the first phase, understanding, thanks to a set of diverse design tools, it was possible to foster an integral characterization of the enterprise, its current situation and its competitive conditions. An integral part of this phase was the analysis of the products and services, the processes and portfolio, and the branding strategies; its users and their interaction with the products and/or services through ethnographic exercises of observation so that, as a whole, the enterprise and its users were understood in the same context.

The tools are designed and distributed along the project so that they complement one another; thus traceability can be guaranteed and a deeper analysis is achieved. The tools are explained according to the emotional intimacy goal and are classified based on the type of tool and the phase where tools were used.

Figure 3. PADI+2013 work sheet.

Source: <http://www.mipymes.gov.co/publicaciones.php?id=935>

UNDERSTANDING	CONCEPTUALIZING	DELIVERING	PHASE / KEY WORDS REGARDING EMOTIONAL INTIMACY TO THE BUSINESS PERSON
Strategic PES			To feel the organization as a living being surrounded by other beings living together in a particular context.
Customer Journey Map			To sensitize in relation with his users and to empathize with them, visualizing their aspirations, hopes and wishes.
Diagnostic Diagram			To confront the reality of his organization as a model.
	Branding Workshop		To define, clarify or reconstruct the identity of his organization. To embody the notion of their users.
	Future Scenario		To envision their future as stimuli for disruptive thinking.
	Action Plan		To motivate to work with concrete actions.
		Strategy and Brand	To gain long-term perspective.
		Portfolio and Process	To translate the strategic perspective.
		Operative	To concretize an action.

Strategic PES

Type of tool: Diagnostic tool

Phase: (1) Understanding

Authors: Totally developed by the work team

Goal: The strategic PES (product, experience and service) (Figure 4) is a tool that allows fast diagnoses of the current situation of the company, understood as a fish that inhabits a specific context.

Description: The fish head defines the strategic direction of the SME, the tail functions as a steering wheel that directs the enterprise to a market of segmented users; in the belly one can find the product and service portfolio, and in the back the installed capacity. The tool allows the businessperson to feel his organization as a living being that has the same cycle any other business has. Additionally, a holistic experience that evidences the synergic condition of the systems that make organizations is created. Finally, this perception allows to evidence that the enterprise is surrounded by peers, that is to say, by other beings living together in a particular context.

Figure 4. Strategic PES (product, experience, and services) tools. The text on the background is intentionally blurred due to a non-disclosure agreement with the SMEs.

Source: Arenas, J.P. and Mejia, J.R. (2011) and work team PADI+2013 (2013).

Customer journey map

Type of tool: Ethnography and observation

Phase: (1) Understanding

Authors: Different authors

Goal: Through the Customer Journey⁴ — CJ —, the PADI+2013 team analyzed, in some cases, the users' interaction with the product and its use and, in others, the users' interaction with the service, so as to understand the consumption experience in each case. This allowed the businessperson to sensitize her or himself in relation with his users and to empathize with them, visualizing their aspirations, hopes, and wishes.

Description: An important part of the work was the approach and understanding of the user; it allowed the team to identify the gap between the image and the identity of the brand.⁵ The CJ was defined as a graphic description of a user's normal day. They were used to understand the way in which the interaction between the user and the product or service of the brand under study is established.

Diagnostic diagram

Type of tool: Diagnostic tool

Phase: (1) Understanding

Authors: Developed by the work team based on different authors

Goal: This diagnosis works like an image that helps the businessperson to confront the reality of his organization as a model that, from the aspirational perspective, stimulates him to carry out the necessary improvements.

Description: When this phase is over, the team has a clear image of the problems and strategic opportunities of the firm, represented in a diagnostic diagram (Figure 6), that balances in the three analysis axes (strategic, tactic, and operative) the current situation of the productive organization. The bigger the triangle, the greater development of the productive organization in that specific axis. After understanding and uncovering the strategic opportunities of the company through the mapping and characterization, the work team starts the second phase, conceptualization, through the development of branding workshops and Future Scenarios — FS — construction.

Figure 5. Customer Journey applied to one of the SME from PADI+2013. The text on the background is intentionally blurred due to a non-disclosure agreement with the SMEs.

Source: PADI+2013 work team.

4. The customer journey map is an oriented graph that describes the journey of a user by representing the different touch-points that characterize his interaction with the service (<http://www.servicedesigntools.org/tools/8>).
5. For PADI+2013 the brand image is understood as the perception users have of the products or the enterprise, contrasted with the brand identity that is the basic enterprise promise and its future objectives as an organization. (De Chernatony, Dall’Olmo, 1998).

Figure 6: Diagnostic diagram for one SME from PADI+2013.

Source: PADI+2013 work team.

Branding workshops

Type of tool: Envisioning tool

Phase: (2) Conceptualizing

Authors: Developed by the work team based on different authors

Goal: In these workshops the businessperson can define, clarify, or reconstruct the identity of her organization, including its products or services.

Description: Co-creative work sessions, known as ‘branding workshops’ were developed. The methodology is based on the rhetoric figure of the personification and consists in the creation of a set of ‘personas’,⁶ starting by the organization, its brand, going to some internal personnel, (salespeople, managers, etc.) and other external personnel (providers, clients, etc.), and even consumption services and experiences. The participation of some enterprise members is crucial, since the most varied the profiles are, the richer the values that can be defined, detected, or analyzed from each one of the created characters. These values are obtained with the help of questions the team posits. The questions help discover the voids (within the organization) and the inconsistencies (the alignment to create brand fidelity); they also help to discover the

6. The personas are archetypes built after an exhaustive observation of the potential users. Each persona is based on a fictional character whose profile gathers up the features of an existing social group. In this way the personas assume the attributes of the groups they represent: from their social and demographic characteristics, to their own needs, desires, habits, and cultural backgrounds (<http://www.servicedesigntools.org/tools/40>).

findings (intervention opportunities). From these ideas, captured in creative sessions, it was possible to generate a strategic concept, so that, as a guiding thread, the strategy, the brand, and the services of the company can be developed.

Future scenarios workshops

Type of tool: Envisioning tool

Phase: (2) Conceptualizing

Authors: Developed by the work team based on different authors

Goal: The FS are a tool that allows, in principle, to identify a set of trends (Figure 8, number 1), that, used as reference, can locate the enterprise in its current strategic position (Figure 8, number 2), to define the future desired position for the organization by the year 2035.

Description: This analysis is framed in a Future Macro Scenario designed as ‘Colombia 2035’, where one articulates the DPEST factors (demographic, political, economic, environmental, and technological). From the blueprint of the national programs mentioned previously, the work was developed with world-class sector organizations,⁷ developing future scenarios specific for the fashion and beauty, innova-

7. These are sectors that have a high demand in the global economy and where Colombia has the chance to grow ten times in each sector in the short run. Eight sectors were defined to lead the strengthening in two areas. The first is called more and better of the good (bad English, what are you trying to say?), under world-class standards. The second is called new and emergent (World class).

Figure 8: Future Scenario for one of the SME from PADI+2013. The text on the background is intentionally blurred due to a non-disclosure agreement with the SMEs.
Source: PADI+2013 work team.

tion and health, and wellbeing sectors. These scenarios act as stimuli for disruptive thinking and help widen the action domains the enterprise has.

Action plan

Type of tool: Planning tool

Phase: (2) Conceptualizing

Authors: Developed by the work team based on different authors

Goal: This plan allows actualizing the work the team wants to perform in favor of the organization, motivating the businessperson to work with concrete actions.

Description: From the diagnostic diagram, the way the enterprise can be supported is analyzed by PADI+2013 in each of the axes through products that, from the design perspective, can support the strategic development of the enterprise.

The team finally concentrates on the development of phase three, delivering, where products, services, and corporate identities are developed, structured in portfolios and supported by strategies. To define the project approach, MADi proposes to focus on the work in three axes that enable the final performance to be determined.

Strategic axis, strategy and brand.

Type of tool: Strategic management and entrepreneurial tool

Phase: (3) Delivering

Authors: Osterwalder, A., and Pigneur, Y. (2010)

Goal: Enables the description, design, challenge, invention, and pivoting of the business model (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010)

Description: It is understood that organizations have a future vision in the strategy, as the set of directions given by the board of directors and included in its mission, vision, and corporate values. For PADI+2013 this axis includes a new or renewed promise of value defined through a business model canvas or a business road map (strategic PES and strategic time line).

Tactic axis, portfolio and processes.

Type of tool: Strategic management and entrepreneurial tool

Phase: (3) Delivering

Authors: Developed by the work team based on different authors

Goal: It is known that strategy must translate in the operative, through a transition space called tactic axis.

Description: For PADI+2013, will include a portfolio of products or services (new or improved) or a system mapping that, for the organization, describes schematically how business opportunities discovered in previous phases are to be handled.

Operative axis.

Type of tool: Strategic management and entrepreneurial tool

Phase: (3) Delivering

Figure 9. Diagnosis and action plan for a SME from PADI+2013.
Source: PADI+2013 work team.

Authors: Developed by the work team based on different authors

Goal: To deliver a comprehensive set of tangible results of the project

Description: To finish the integral branding solution, the operative axis is considered. It includes product, space, communication, or service, where operations are understood as the way in which previously developed strategies and tactics are implemented. The PADI+2013 is capable of delivering technical cards (product, space, or communication), or a service blueprint identifying the most important touch points so that the design team can define which should be developed in detail.

Results PADI+2013

The development of the PADI+2013 results were essential to validate the MADI proposal in which, through the use of empathy and emotional intimacy, better results in design knowledge transfer processes for Colombian SME can be obtained. In function of the objective as the application of MADI and in two levels, as a knowledge transfer exercise and as a project with a social impact, this project achieved:

Through empathy and emotional intimacy, the work team achieved, in an effective, efficient and successful way, a knowledge transfer process to business people and their organizations to strengthen the acquisition of design thinking knowledge in the business environment and to better understand their own enterprises and their dynamics, making evident their strengths

and weaknesses. Since the team was formed by different design specialties, it was capable of developing projects with diverse levels of complexity for enterprises in different sectors, sizes, and with different design knowledge levels. This allowed constructing knowledge transfer participatory strategies that suit each organization's needs and propose a rhythm and scope for each of them.

All this is corroborated through processes started by enterprises in the short term. Three of the participant enterprises have already invested in projects derived from PADI+2013; one of them, in the medical sector that offers gynecology and obstetrics services, implemented an improvement in the customer service area in order to offer a more empathic service experience, thanks to the creative team recommendations, drawing near not only the mother but the entire family nearer to a unique experience with the baby.

A relevant aspect in the project is the adequate proportion between the number of participants, three for each organization and six for the PADI+2013; this arrangement made possible for part of the transferred knowledge to arise from participatory, discovery, 'learning by doing' methods, working on each enterprise's solutions space.

One of the achievements was for design to be understood as a prospective exercise capable of creating future scenarios that will guide the enterprises' strategic development. Besides, design was understood as a discipline based on the visual synthesis capability that allows solving complex problems and gives tangible results and as a human centered innovation

process that, through systematic and constant testing, using models and prototypes, diminishes the risk and uncertainty levels in enterprises' investment projects.

In terms of geographical and sectorial coverage, PADI+2013 worked with four institutional projects, fourteen SMEs located in Bogotá, and six in Cartagena (eight micro, eight small and four medium sized enterprises). They are from six PTP-MinCIT⁸ world class sectors, and seven prioritized sectors by the CCB⁹ and the CCCT¹⁰ that represent more than 920 employees supported by the project that, in sum, mean more than 144.000 legal minimum monthly wages in Colombia.

Six of the participant SMEs have escalated PADI+2013 results to their boards of directors and are looking for financing for the development of the projects. Four of these have already started brand, product, or packaging development projects that have involved the hiring of diverse specialized designers.

The social impact of this model can be understood from two different perspectives. One is related with the micro business people and the way in which the new transferred knowledge changes the enterprise's perception, its products and services; a new holistic look, integrated and visual, allows businesses to construct relations that were not clear up to this moment. Another social impact is related to the final impact on users and involves communities that turn the enterprise into a generator of sustainable development.

CONCLUSIONS, RECOMMENDATIONS AND PROJECTIONS ON MADI

Emotions in knowledge transfer

From the results obtained in PADI+2013, we can see that in MADI, empathy and emotional intimacy in the 'tutoring model' are the ideal knowledge transfer strategies compared with traditional consulting.

The work process included emotional components that resulted in products, services, and experiences with a human centered perspective that shows their emotional understanding; that is why it is considered important that in future initiatives based on MADI experts use intensively the emotional design methodologies to enhance the impacts on enterprises.

The formulation of bigger solution spaces is recommended; in these places should intervene not only the direct actors involved (organizations and work team) but also external actors like the State and other institutions to achieve a more dynamic process development that helps improve citizens' lives and

8. The sectors were: software, information technologies, health and well being tourism, cosmetics and cleaning goods, metallurgical, steel and shipyard, fashion system and dairy. Footwear, leather and leather goods clusters, creative and content industries and clothing.

9. Chamber of Commerce of Bogotá.

10. Chamber of Commerce of Cartagena de Indias.

the innovation and entrepreneurial ecosystem in the country. Along this line of thought, MADI could be the conceptual base for the development of projects of the kind of Living Lab, where citizens play an essential role in the project and become an active element of the solutions space.

The Living Lab project, as the logical MADI's next step projection, must be an appealing possibility for different kinds of public, parapublic, and private sectors, basically because the use of the Human Centered Design (or Citizen Centered Design) approach will increase the chance for SMEs to explore new markets and increase their capabilities as competitive, effective, and efficient organizations.

Adding to the Living Lab, and regarding MADI's projections, the project and its approach is ready to be scalable thanks to its modularity and its capability of being adjusted and fixed to the needs and requirements (cultural differences, social development, etc.) of the new context of work. It is willing to be developed in other cities and geographical spots different than Bogota or Cartagena. Chambers of Commerce, the local government and municipalities are key actors in order to guarantee the appropriate development of the project in each new location.

On the other hand MADI, as a knowledge transfer model, is able to contribute to the industrial development of other Latin American countries due to its similarities in terms of the inner-culture of its productive sector. Pacific Alliance is one potential opportunity due to organization goals that include economic integration between countries.

Social innovation and contextualized design for SMEs in Colombia

MADI conceives design as an integral intervention that provides brand solution spaces through four big values: empathy, prospecting, visual synthesis, and prototyping; all of them of great value for Colombian SMEs, especially for micro enterprises.¹¹

SMEs, as the base for the entrepreneurial fabric, represent a bet on the future because of their strategic relevance expressed in the huge impact they have on economic indicators, since they generate 81% of the country's workforce. The tutoring projects for enterprises derived from MADI, because of their nature, should not be massive; instead, it is recommended that projects develop strategies to replicate, in a viral way, knowledge transfer based on the diffusion to other organizations, enterprises, employees, and users.

For future versions, it is recommended to extend the duration of the tutoring process, to rely on a digital tool (wiki), and to widen the scope of the Productive Transformation Program — PTP — sectors to work with: ecotourism, hortifruitculture, auto parts, vehicles, and chocolaterie and its raw materials; so that design thinking is established

11. Defined by MinCIT as the enterprise that has up to ten employees and total actives, excluding real estate, inferior to 500 minimum monthly wages (\$160.000 USD, aprox.)

transversely in the country's business development. It is also important to strengthen the work team by hiring new, more specialized, profiles with a more technical formation.

To sum up, the initiatives formulated from MADI, including PADI+2013, posit a positive scenario for the use of design to benefit the country's industrial reconversion; they intervene positively in communities that live in a symbiotic way with organizations, making them more competitive and innovative.

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ENHANCING THE VALUE OF SOCIAL INNOVATION: INTRODUCING THE ‘PEOPLE VALUE CANVAS’ TO SUPPORT DESIGNERS IN VALUE CREATION

Sabine E Wildevuur

Head Creative Care Lab, Waag Society/Researcher, VU University Amsterdam

✉ sabine@waag.org, s.wildevuur@vu.nl

Dick van Dijk

Waag Society

✉ dick@waag.org

Marise Schot

Waag Society

✉ marise@waag.org

ABSTRACT

Well-designed interactive experiences connect people, meet their needs, life-styles and life choices, and can make a positive difference on their wellbeing. The overall challenge of people-centred innovation can be summarised in how to design value for people — as well as for companies and society. To be able to create value, designers need to explore, validate and reflect upon the different design choices and their intended impact. In turn, this demands methods for understanding needs and motivations of the users, exploring solutions and designing business models. There isn't one single way to organise these tasks. Nevertheless, it may be helpful to learn from frameworks that offer a basic recipe consisting of checklists and a structure for the work to be done.

In this paper, we introduce a concept development tool to support value creation for both designers and stakeholders, which we call People Value Canvas (PVC), according to which users' needs and wishes can be systematically identified for the purpose of the further conceptualization of innovative solutions with a technological component. The PVC is intended for designers and stakeholders involved in social innovation, and who are interested in how media ICT can be employed to promote design for social interaction. We approached the PVC as a reflective, systematic tool during the design process. The tool proved valuable in discussing new concepts since it gave structure to constructive conversations and showed the interdependencies between the different design aspects. Additional research will help to understand this even more.

KEYWORDS: *Social innovation, value creation, healthy ageing, empathic design, media ICT*

INTRODUCTION

'Social innovation' refers to new strategies, concepts, ideas and organizations that strive to provide solutions for serious social challenges (Stikker, 2012). The urgency of today's social innovation is mobilized by the innovation capacities of everyone in society. Social innovation now is founded on a fundamentally different value system than it was in the 20th century. Social innovation can best be described as striving towards a society that is sustainable and socially conscious. Innovative solutions addressing this challenge ask for new ways of working, often referred to as 'creative research' (Van Dijk, 2011), aiming to involve a variety of stakeholders in co-creative acts; these include universities, research centres,

schools, healthcare organizations, network providers, governments, artists, living labs, innovative small and medium-sized enterprises, and large corporations.

To provide value, the long-term effects of interactions and experiences of design solutions have to be considered by designers, for which a framework such as the Framework of Product Experience could be of value (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007). This theoretical framework structured attempts to 'design for experience. To be able to substantiate value and compare different value propositions, designers need to be able to challenge existing concepts and to collectively imagine and build future scenarios, together with other stakeholders. This requires an open attitude and sensibility of the designers to fully understand the questions at hand and the

users that are involved. In practice, despite all the best intentions, products, solutions and/or services often seem to be conceived in relative isolation, not realizing the optimal long-term impact for its target group. Designers have a diverse set of methods and tools at their disposal to help them explore the potential value their interventions could bring to people, and to bring the people they serve through design directly into the design process in order to better meet their needs in the future (Sanders, 2012).

Value creation demands a process of understanding needs and motivations of the users, exploring solutions and designing business models. There isn't one single way to organise these tasks, nevertheless it may be helpful to learn from frameworks that offer a basic recipe: checklists and a structure according to which the work will be done. A 'canvas', such as the popular Business Model Canvas, has already proven to be a useful tool in analysing innovation processes (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010). Nevertheless, most of the business models we know lack detailed knowledge about individuals, making them operate on assumptions about 'their customers' that don't reflect their real needs and motivations. Even though the people behind the Business Model Canvas developed an additional 'Value Proposition Canvas', which helps you design, test, and build your company's Value Proposition for customers in a more structured and thoughtful way, the users needs are addressed from the company's point of view and not from the user's point of view ('Value Proposition Canvas', 2012). We developed the People Value Canvas in an iterative manner, born out of a need to describe critical aspects of concept development, involving a technological component. When users, designers, researchers, and business developers work together, each of them take on multiple roles throughout the design process. However, the user is the expert on his own life and experiences, and should therefore be the driver of the development process. The People Value Canvas supports this angle of the design process by offering a tool to systematically identify users' needs and wishes for the purpose of further conceptualizing innovative solutions with a technological component.

EMPATHY AS A VALUE CONSOLIDATION TOOL

One of the biggest challenges of modern day society is the aging population. We advocate a people value approach as a perspective on the challenge of ageing. It is based on our work in the Express to Connect project (E2C), an Ambient Assisted Living project, which looked for ICT-based solutions for the advancement of social interaction of elderly people (Wildevuur et al., 2011). The oldest age bracket in the population is at particular risk of becoming isolated and lonely as they grow older and their work-related networks erode. ICT-based solutions could advance social interaction amongst older adults. A user-driven approach was used from the beginning of the project, actively involving users from the start (Wildevuur et al., 2013). The E2C partners jointly proposed a people-centred, holistic approach towards designing solu-

tions for the ageing society, in order to deal with what really matters: social connectedness between people. Therefore, it was important to find ways to reframe 'old' ideas, step aside from assumptions regarding 'old age' and to reconfigure the design process towards a more empathic approach.

Since there did not seem to be a tool which mapped insights in a structured way from the user value perspective, the urge was felt to construct such a tool based on our own experiences: the People Value Canvas (PVC). The central idea behind the canvas is that a product or service has added value only when it satisfies user needs and fits user motivations. On the one hand, the canvas helps to structure user insights (needs, context and so on) (figure 3). On the other hand, PVC describes the proposed new technological solution (effect, experience and so on) (figure 4). We connected the People Value Canvas closely to the logic of the Business Model Canvas (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010). The Business Model Canvas (BMC) has become a popular strategic management and entrepreneurial tool, which allows the user to design a business model in a user-friendly way. A 'canvas', such as the popular Business Model Canvas, has already proven to be a useful tool in analysing innovation processes. The BMC formally describes nine building blocks for the activities. Since the release of the canvas, new canvases for specific niches have been developed. The overall output of the PVC is a value proposition, which is the starting point of the Business Model Canvas (see: figure 1). The filled out PVC can help establish the entire scope of the intervention you design, often referred to as the 'Product-Service-System' (PSS).

When working towards the business model of a product or service, one has to envisage how it will be implemented in real life and how it will sustain itself. The business model is part of the business strategy. What does the market for your product look like? Who will be involved? What value does the product create, for whom and why? Who is going to invest and pay, and what is the flow of monetary reward? The Business Model Canvas is an effective way to capture this discussion, and to support sketching, developing and discussing business model elements within the development team. At the centre of the business model canvas is the value proposition: Which customer's problems and needs are being served?

Qualitative insights into why, how, and when people experience a problem or have unmet needs is necessary when aiming to address these problems or unlock opportunities, and might prove a critical factor in triggering their ability or willingness to use new products or services, which are developed according to the users needs and wishes. Critical insights are the relevant needs, the different user characteristics, their contexts, and the motivations that drive them. The PVC is therefore intrinsically linked to the development principles of the 'Users as Designers' method, as well as the ethnographic research method (Van Dijk, 2011). Users as Designers is a combination of existing and customised participatory and empathic design methods that are qualitative in nature and are drawn from the arts and social sciences. This design philosophy is particularly appropriate when challenging user

Figure 1: People Value Canvas (People) in relation to Business Model Canvas (Value Proposition)

groups are involved, such as seniors and their caregivers. Inspirational research methods help to facilitate the dialogue needed to elicit personal and contextual information that helps to define users' needs and desires. Conscientiously involving the users throughout the design and development process helps designers to build strong empathic relationships and intimate connections with exemplary users. During the development process, users tend to be involved in various (co-creative) ways; different approaches are available for designers to involve them. The PVC uses a number of these tools and methods to help designers fill out the canvas. In the explanation of the building blocks, some of these methods will be described briefly.

PEOPLE VALUE CANVAS: NINE BUILDING BLOCKS TO REFLECT ON VALUE

The People Value Canvas consists of nine building blocks—that have to be filled in when developing new concepts—describing the input that has to be provided in order to establish the value proposition for the user (See: figure 2). The building blocks are intrinsically linked and have to be revisited iteratively. The framework has been developed in an iterative manner within the earlier mentioned Express to Connect-project.

Figure 2. The People Value Canvas

Figure 3. Gather user insights

When you take the interdependencies between the different blocks into consideration, this structure allows for a holistic development and description of concepts. The different building blocks have been iteratively formed and grouped during the development process. The descriptions provided below describe what needs to be considered during concept development in order to reflect upon value.

Roughly the canvas is divided into a 'user insights' part (see: figure 3) and 'intervention' part. The first part is based on the conducted user research whilst the second part describes the envisioned intervention.

Building block I: People

Who are you designing for? People take centre stage in the user value canvas. Designing for social innovation means designing innovative products, systems, or services that help people to be active, joyful and socially connected to society, which in turn effectively contributes to their health, overall quality of life, and social inclusion. To really understand your target audience they need to be regarded as a source not only for research, but also for inspiration, co-creation, and prototyping. A clear demarcation of the people you are designing for makes it possible to initiate multifaceted design research that provides deeper insights into needs, motivation, and characteristics.

Building block II: Needs

What are the most urgent or specific needs you aim to address? People have all sorts of needs. People need to feel related to others in order to feel socially connected. People need input to take informed decisions. There are several models we could use to look at needs, such as Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs (Maslow & Lowry, 1968), Design for Happi-

ness (Schot et al., 2009) and McClelland's Human Motivation Theory (McClelland, 1987), to name but a few; but when exploring social innovation we tend to look at six dimensions of wellbeing as a starting point: the physical, spiritual, intellectual, social, emotional, and occupational dimensions (Renger et al., 2000). However, there are several needs frameworks that you can use as a reference point to categorize the needs of your target group. Nonetheless, keep in mind that there might be conflicting needs (Ozkaramanli & Desmet, 2012).

Building block III: Characteristics

What are the attributes of the people for whom we are designing? In what ways are they socially active and connected? What are their lives like? What kind of relationship do they have with others and with technology?

The insights arising from qualitative research can be channelled into 'portraits'. Much like a 'persona', a portrait is a description of your audience, but based on empirical data from your qualitative research rather than a fictive description. Portraits anchor the differences within the identified user needs. These portraits serve as: vehicles for empathy and identification; visual depictions of knowledge and information; and representations of certain market segments.

Building block IV: Motivation

What is a person's attitude in life? What are the relevant user motivations that might stimulate or hinder potential interventions? Motivation is what drives a person to behave in a certain way, and is in that sense different or complementary to the needs: motivation is the crucial component in setting and reaching goals. Motivations shed light on individual aspirations, and what people value. Intrinsic motivation is driven by an interest or enjoyment in the task itself, and exists within

Figure 4. Describing the intervention

the individual, rather than relying on external pressures or rewards. Motivation may be rooted in a basic need to minimize physical pain and maximize pleasure; or it may come from specific needs such as eating and resting; or a desired object, goal, state of being, or ideal; or it may be attributed to less apparent reasons such as altruism, selfishness, morality, or avoiding mortality.

Building block V: Context

In which context does an intervention need to land? The way a person approaches, uses and experiences an innovation needs to be seen in a broader context, which includes not just the user and the product or service, but also other contextual factors (time, place, temperature and so on). Important contextual parameters include people's life circumstances, such as income, geography (urban or rural), and distance from family members, but also the location where the product or service is used, or where a person's comfort zone is. Context mapping and social mapping are tools to visualize all these factors from the user's perspective, and to get a first notion of what opportunities and/or limitations they face.

Building block VI: Technology

When you want to put people and experiences at the centre of developing solutions supported through technology, you need to be explicit about your technological development (see figure 4). The design space in a technology-driven approach is often limited, since the outcome (the technology) is frequently defined in advance. Disruptive solutions do not get a chance. Different media allow for different degrees of participation on the part of a person who chooses to use them, and can emphasise one sense (for example sight or hearing) over the others. This makes it very important to choose the right set of design principles when the systems that influence

our lives are being built. Think of how this particular technology will take the users into account and specifically their desire to feel trusted, socially accepted or connected. A good interface activates people, enables them to take action themselves, empowers them, and offers a context for dialogue. In order to create real value we should put empowerment, reciprocity, and transparency at the very core of the design of processes and interactions. Openness allows people to take control of their own systems, and find new uses for them. The right to access and use the (aggregated) data should be the same for both the user and the system. This goes beyond the issue of privacy, which should be designed carefully at the heart of every system. The answer to building block 'Technology' is a balanced description of the technology envisioned, with an openness to spot potential unintended side effects that might occur during its use.

Building block VII: Process

What are the potential consequences and desired touch points related to the envisioned intervention? Offering an experience means paying attention to the entire ecosystem within which the application or service is located. For instance, support: there is no point developing an alarm button in the absence of an emergency room with people who cannot react to the alarm. Moreover, interactions with an application usually involve multiple touch points, and services around the product. 'Service Design' is a discipline that offers a variety of tools to this end (Stickdorn et al., 2011). These include methods such as the 'Service Blueprint', which aims to develop a service prototype by looking at all the conditions to ensure that technology works in real life and not just in the test environment. The answer to building block 'Process' is a reflection on the potential challenges and desired touch points related to the intervention you envision – some visible to the user, some very much in the background.

Building block VIII: Experience

What is the quality of your interaction? How digital or tactile is it? How is it connected to the user's daily life, routines and flow? Will it contribute to the sovereignty of the user? Some pleasurable experiences can be described with a flow model and theory, describing the optimal mental state (flow or zone) where people reach enjoyment and engagement in an activity (Csikszentmihalyi, 1997). Increased understanding of human drives and pleasures will help to understand how interactive experiences can be designed to have a positive impact and can play a positive role in social interaction. Throughout the experience design process, storytelling plays an important role as a tool for empathy, inspiration, contextualisation and explanation. Intuitive interfaces, playful learning and embodied interaction can help to create pleasurable experiences. The answer to building block 'Experience' is a vivid description of the nature of the experience you design from the perspective of the user.

Building block IX: Effect

What will be the long-term impact of your intervention on the user's own narrative? How will the intervention contribute to their potential or relations? Social innovations are supposed to support social change, since their aim is to stimulate new experiences and behaviours that meet social needs of all kinds, raise the individual's quality of life, and create value for society as a whole. On the other hand, some (assistive) technology can cause existing skills or knowledge to become obsolete.

Social innovators need to be aware of the implications of their designs, both in terms of their sustainability and of their transformative power, i.e. their impact on people's lives. To determine their relevance to people's lives, processes and routines, an estimate of their long-term effects is needed. In the context of people value, the effect of a solution is measured in terms of its contribution to wellbeing. The answer to building block 'Effect' is an estimate of the anticipated impact of the intervention.

EVALUATION

The first versions of PVC were developed iteratively based upon the Ambient Assisted Living-project, Express to Connect. In several workshops the base of a design tool was developed to work in a systematic way with different stakeholders, such as prospective users (the primary target group are not only the people over the age of 65, but also their children and grandchildren), municipalities, SMEs, and developers.

As a follow-up to the E2C effort, the PVC-tool was used in different settings; the designers collaboratively developed the concept iteratively while filling out the canvas. Different tools like portraits were introduced to support the designers to identify user needs (Wildevuur et al., 2013).

When trying out the canvas in the workshops almost all participants recognised the canvas to be a useful tool, which helped them feel more in control in tackling all aspects concerning the value proposition, since it provided an overview and a common ground for discussion. One participant said that he did not feel he found new surprising insights because of the tool, but he could definitely see his concept had improved. Other participants agreed upon the fact that the tool supported them so naturally that they could use it intuitively. Moreover, the tool provided a framework that would help them in the whole process. In a nutshell, the canvas seemed to be relevant for a designer and stakeholders as a checklist, but most of all the canvas was helpful as a communication tool for collaborative developing.

CONCLUSION

In this paper we approached the PVC as a reflective, systematic tool during the design process. Apart from applying the canvas to design processes, the PVC has also been tested and used in different settings as a tool for developing a mutual understanding between different stakeholders on the development of a concept, design or service. The tool proved valuable in discussing new concepts as it gave structure to constructive conversations and showed the interdependencies between the different design aspects. Filling out the canvas—in a digital format or printed as a poster, to be filled with sticky notes—can therefore be helpful in a collaborative process with different stakeholders. Additional research will help to understand this even more.

Our mission is to design for the 'real needs of real people', and our aim is the empowerment of the target group. The biggest challenge is: How to develop and formulate models of value propositions? The PVC is a supporting tool that strives towards this goal. PVC is a value tool that can substantiate value by mapping the context of a target user to the different aspects of a concept. It can also be used to develop a concept, and to provide a reference point when choices need to be made later on in the development process, or to help frame the ideas around the possible impact of a solution. In a nutshell, the PVC supports the designer in creating impact for the user by challenging the proposed solution by asking the following questions: Does the product/service truly fulfil the user's needs? Does it fit their lifestyle? What is the impact of the required technology? Will it be accepted/understood by the user, and what will the expected long-term effect(s) be on individual lives as well as society as a whole?

All together, the canvas reveals which information is lacking in the context and supports the design of a product or service; the 'blind spots' become visible. The canvas can help to compare the added value of different conceptual directions, to reflect on the crucial aspects of a concept, to engage in further research on a target group, or to guide the design of emerging solutions.

DISCUSSION

Filling out the PVC helps designers and stakeholders to reflect on the impact of the intervention they are designing. To consolidate value, a designer needs to empathize with its users to understand their true needs and to validate its concept on how it fits the users' needs and context. Tools to support the designer and stakeholders on these aspects seem important. As the set of tools is growing rapidly, a categorization to understand when and why to apply those tools seems to be essential. PVC could be regarded as a reflective tool, next to empathy tools (such as Portraits), or consolidation tools (such as Service Blueprints). These are all part of a large toolkit, which are already available to designers. A more elaborate categorization, and in-depth research, is needed to identify the different tools and their role and function in the process of designing for social innovation.

Just as the Business Model Canvas is not the complete answer to developing a successful business model, the People Value Canvas is not the complete answer to creating value for the user. Rather, it is a method to support designers and stakeholders in a systematic manner to gain insight into what people actually consider to be valuable. In addition, PVC could be used in user sessions, co. creation workshops, expert panels, and rapid prototyping meetings in order to exchange knowledge, communicate ideas, and ultimately learn from one another. When designers and stakeholders work together in the design process, they all take different roles. When working in multidisciplinary teams, the People Value Canvas could map the space for social innovation. However, additional research is preferred on the PVC with different users, to clarify the different building blocks, and to avoid confusion about terminology or how to use it. To do so, a team of universities (of applied sciences), SMEs and other organisations are developing an educational module based upon PVC for international students as a framework to walk through a specific design challenge and map insights in an iterative and new manner.

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STUDYING RETAIL DESIGN THROUGH A CROSS-CULTURAL PERSPECTIVE

Ann Petermans

Faculty of Architecture and arts, Hasselt University, Diepenbeek, Belgium

✉ ann.petermans@uhasselt.be

Ammin Gil Huerta

Faculty of Architecture, National Autonomous University of Mexico, Mexico

✉ ammingil@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This paper proposes an approach to doing research in retail design, based on theoretical viewpoints and methodologies close to the realm of interior architects and retail designers. In particular, it focuses on the question of how to study customer experiences with regard to actual stores' retail design, with the help of the Experience Web. The authors use the Experience Web to discuss the results of a cross-cultural study on customer experiences, whereby the authors, both from their proper cultural background, immersed themselves in twenty-three actual retail environments located in different Belgian shopping cities.

We argue that the research method of 'subjective personal introspection' (SPI) generates valuable exploratory perspectives on the study of customer experiences, which can be particularly relevant in the early stages of a qualitative, interpretive research process. According to the authors, SPI's potential lies in uncovering subjective and complex meanings that people attribute to experiences.

KEYWORDS: *Experiences, Experience Web, Subjective Personal Introspection, Cross-cultural Perspective, Interior Architecture.*

INTRODUCTION

Imagine a Mexican woman who's visiting Belgium, walking through the historic city center of Antwerp. She has a particular interest in retail design, so one of the first things that catches her attention is the design of Belgian retail environments. What she learned after one day of strolling around in Antwerp, is that many of the fashion brand stores there seem exactly the same as in Mexico City: the store design, the product offerings, the behavior of the personnel, even the profile of personnel working in the stores here seemed perfectly similar to her familiar Mexican experiences. Indeed, the globalized fashion industry impacts on the way that strategies of clothing brands are being translated into the design of their retail environments. Since geographical and cultural limits between countries seem to be diluting, cultural barriers are disappearing. Products thus are becoming more 'international'. In the authors' viewpoints, experience design has to be involved with these kinds of cultural considerations.

In today's experience economy, retailers and manufacturers agree that whether selling to individual customers or corporations, offering only goods and services is no longer satisfying.

As consumers often perceive products and services as homogeneous, retail stakeholders are being forced to look out for differentiation strategies. Triggering memorable 'customer experiences' in retail environments, where multiple tangible and intangible stimuli can interact (Carù & Cova, 2003, 2007; Klingmann, 2008; Petermans & Van Cleempoel, 2010a, 2010b), seems to offer interesting perspectives. Working on and investing in customer experience, however, might not seem an obvious priority in a relatively uncertain economic environment where consumers all over the world have become more particular about what they will buy. Nevertheless, research has indicated that customer experiences can encourage store and retailer loyalty (Pullman & Gross, 2004), indicating that a loyal customer base is a retailer's most valuable defense against recessionary pressures.

Despite the growing recognition of the importance of customer experiences in retail practice, academic literature focusing on this topic often lacks conceptualization of central concepts and empirical support (Jüttner et al., 2009; Verhoef et al., 2009; Petermans & Van Cleempoel, 2010b). Indeed, 'experience' as such is an abstract concept to gain insight into. Moreover, existing research on the customer-retail environment relationship, performed in academic disciplines

related to retail design, seems not to appeal to designers (Petermans & Van Cleempoel, 2010b). As different authors in the last decades have indicated that interior architecture lacks a specific body of knowledge, especially in relationship to architecture (Abercrombie, 1990; Marshall-Baker, 2000; Clemons & Eckman, 2008), Edwards (2011) pleads for combining the advancement of the discipline's theoretical knowledge base with insights into the actual design practices. Aiming to answer Edwards' recent call, the purpose of this paper is twofold: (i) to reflect on retail design, customer experiences, and the importance of cross-cultural issues in studying retail environments via a review of literature; (ii) to use the Experience Web, a tool to gain insight into customer experiences, as a means to analyze customer experiences from a cross-cultural perspective in a qualitative, exploratory study. When we report about the cross-cultural studies that were performed, we bring the three concepts presented in the literature review together: with the help of the Experience Web, the authors separately reflect about their experiences in the same sample of Belgian retail environments wherein they both immersed themselves, with particular attention for cross-cultural issues. We conclude the paper by pointing to the importance of applying a holistic research attitude when trying to understand how people experience a certain environment and the role of cross-cultural aspects in this respect.

LITERATURE REVIEW: RETAIL DESIGN, CUSTOMER EXPERIENCES AND CROSS-CULTURAL ISSUES IN STUDYING RETAIL ENVIRONMENTS

Retail design

The term 'retail design' covers several issues that need to be considered when designing commercial interiors, ranging from aesthetic, financial and legislative aspects, to understanding how the designed interior will perform functionally and commercially (Petermans & Van Cleempoel, 2010a). As a research niche, retail design has gained status in retail management, but is still an emerging discipline in the field of interior architecture. Retail design as a scientific discipline is influenced by several background disciplines. These disciplines can not only offer valuable theoretical insights from which retail design may well benefit, but they can also offer empirical and methodological insights. Disciplines such as psychology, marketing, and consumer behavior have already focused on studying the relationship between the user and the commercial environment (Mehrabian & Russell, 1974; Donovan & Rossiter, 1982; Turley & Milliman, 2000). These types of studies however mostly consider and approach retail and interior architecture as a sum of isolated parameters, which can also be studied as such. This approach however does not correspond to designers' viewpoints. They are convinced that the final effects of single variables are dependent upon people's evaluation of the *total* environment (Nelson & Stolterman, 2003; Holm, 2006; Petermans & Van Cleempoel, 2010b). Spaces that need to be designed or studied need to be approached as holistic totalities, as 'wholes' where various elements interact and

determine how people feel and behave in a space. Consumers' overall perceptions about a certain store also seem to influence their overall preference for that store (Thang & Tan, 2003). Therefore, today there is an increased interest for doing research in retail settings more 'holistically', whereby one aims to be able to explain how consumers process the entire in-store atmosphere (Healy et al., 2007; Sands, 2008).

Customer experiences

In the last two decades, 'experience' truly has become a buzzword in retail-related discussions. In communication about retail and in concrete retail design, the concept is continuously being used as a means or a tool for differentiation. However, talking about the concrete contents of experience has never been easy. Indeed, what is experience, and how can it be assessed in retail and interior architecture? An extensive literature review showed that various disciplines have ascribed different meanings to the concept (Carù & Cova, 2003; Sleswijk-Visser, 2009). As a consequence, there is no general consensus about its definition (Sleswijk-Visser, 2009).

To counter these remarks, the first author developed the Experience Web (see Figure 1). This 'tool' has been developed in an attempt to conceptualize customer experiences; (a) while building on the insights of the literature on aspects of customer experience and in-store behavior; and (b) approaching the concept with a vocabulary and research methodologies close to the realm of interior architects.

In a recent publication (Petermans et al., 2013), we discussed the conceptualization and contents of the Experience Web in its full detail. In the 2013 publication, we not only theoretically reflect about the Web; we also confront the theoretical conceptualization with the connotations of relevant stakeholders with regard to the aspects containing the Experience Web.

Length restraints oblige us here to give a short summary of the contents of Figure 1.

With the Experience Web, we want to indicate that experience is always a subjective response that people have towards products, services, and the different elements that make part of a designed space. Experiences are always time and context specific, and can involve multiple communication channels. They are also spread over a period of time (before, during, and after an experience). Taking into account that prior experiences can influence future ones, experiences are also dynamic. As experiences entail different kinds of processes and responses, which are affected by (interactions between) aspects of the designed environment, situation, and user characteristics, experiences are holistic.

The aspects summarized in the upper part of Figure 1 indicate that customer experiences are influenced by aspects or elements that a designer or another involved stakeholder can control, but also by elements that are outside a stakeholder's control (e.g., subjective character of experiences). As a consequence, stakeholders can never fully control the occurrence of experiences; they can only try to create and manage their contexts.

Figure 1. The Experience Web

When trying to design for these conditions, aspects of experience in the lower part of Figure 1 come to the fore. When designing for experience, stakeholders — certainly in the retail industry — intentionally try to stage an experience. In practice, most companies choose to concentrate on a particular theme or narrative that characterizes them and that appeals to their target audience. In this process, one often uses elements of Pine and Gilmore’s ‘experience realms’ (1999). Companies need to pay particular attention that every possible controllable aspect of a company’s offering is consistent with the chosen theme, and appeals as much as possible to their customers’ senses. Emotion and value-orientation are also inextricably bound up with customer experiences. When designing an environment with the aim to trigger experiences, designers and retailers need to pay attention not only to hedonic aspects but equally to utilitarian (functional) aspects. In the end, retailers and designers who try to design for experience mostly strive to involve the customer at different levels (e.g., cognitive and affective), and immerse them in

the designed environment by engaging or connecting with them in a personal way. Finally, experiences can also be, or become, memorable.

As our conceptualization of customer experience clarifies, trying to understand the complex nature of customer experiences in actual retail environments makes it essential to go beyond a view on experience as something simple and readily managed (Carù & Cova, 2007).

Cross-cultural issues in studying retail environments

The need to understand cross-cultural topics has become a central issue in several disciplines, and specifically in retail design. In order to develop ‘appropriate’ retail design, it seems necessary to understand customer behaviour, which has changed dramatically in recent decades. Indeed, amongst other factors, new patterns of consumer behaviour have been shaped due to changes in political boundaries, advances in communications technology, commerce, and regional integration. Beyond the

limits of a country, consumers are increasingly subject to a variety of influences; national consumer cultures are diluting and giving way to global hegemony. On the other hand, ethnic and nationalist identities have emerged, resulting in a greater market fragmentation (Douglas & Craig, 1997).

Many factors influence changing customer behaviour. In what follows, we dive deeper into some factors that are relevant for our research purposes. Today, consumers massively migrate from underdeveloped countries to developed countries. Many Chinese consumers for instance migrate to the United States and Europe, and many Latin American consumers (mainly Mexican and Colombian people) migrate to the United States (Douglas & Craig, 1997). In addition, consumers nowadays have the ability to be 'physically mobile' and travel all over the world, which exposes them to new lifestyles, products, and patterns of behaviour. Consumers are also increasingly 'virtually mobile'. Consumer behaviour is thus steadily being permeated by new and diverse influences; therefore, studying cross-cultural issues has become a challenging research topic, certainly in the area of retail and retail design.

In order to understand cross-cultural topics, it is important to define what culture is. According to McCort and Malhotra (1993, p. 97), in Soares (2007, p. 277), culture is 'the complex whole which includes knowledge, belief, art, morals, custom and any other capabilities and habit acquired by man as a member of society', and according to Hofstede (1993, p.89), culture is 'the collective programming of the mind that distinguished one group or category of people from another'. Although it has been generally taken for granted that culture is extremely stable, there is considerable empirical evidence that clearly indicates that cultures change much more often and rapidly than previously thought (Steel & Taras, 2010).

There are various cultural frameworks and models described in academic literature, but for our purposes, Hofstede's work is particularly valuable. Using a large international sample, Hofstede (1984, 1991, 2001) created five dimensions, assigned indexes on each to all nations, and linked the dimensions with demographic, geographic, economic, and political aspects of a society (Soares, 2007). Taken into account Hofstede's work, it is relevant for our research purposes to briefly point to some interesting differences between Belgian and Mexican culture. According to Ortíz and Hernández López (n.d.), Belgian and Dutch culture is individualistic, low power distance, and rather feminine, whereas Mexican culture is collectivistic, high power distance, and more masculine. Hofstede also identified that self-actualization is a goal in individualistic countries. Collectivist societies seek other goals, such as harmony and consensus (Ortíz et al., 2013).

When we link these theories to retail design, we are convinced that retail environments are an important medium in which the cross-cultural aspects are worthy to be taken into account. Fowler et al. (2007) agree in their study about Hispanic customers in store environments. In their viewpoint, the human dimension (interaction with staff, staff attitude, language spoken) is the most important atmospheric dimension in a retail environment. Also Davis et al. (2008) state that culture is an

important influence on customers' responses to store atmospherics. Kim (1999), in Davis et al. (2008) argues that ideally the customer interface with a store should be designed so that the store attracts and retains customers across cultures; this position might be seen as a design uniformity across regions, and it'd enable shoppers at different locations to receive a consistent retail environment. However, this strategy doesn't allow regional retailers to capitalize on local themes appealing to specific market segments (Fowler et al., 2007).

In addition, shopping behavior is open to be influenced by the norms of the social group with which one identifies (Ackerman & Tellis, 2001), and shopping habits vary across countries (Millan & Howard, 2007). Also, as Millan and Howard (2007) state, the experiences sought at the mall may also be influenced by a country's economic circumstances. Culture and the state of a country's economy may moderate the level of hedonic and utilitarian shopping motives and experiences. High levels of hedonic shopping experiences may be encountered in developed consumer societies, but may be less prevalent or noticeably absent in less developed economies.

Studying customer experiences in retail environments with the help of subjective personal introspection

Methodology: subjective personal introspection (SPI)

Ethnography is a research approach, which relies on entering people's natural life worlds while aiming to interpret the complexity of human experiences. As ethnographic methodologies allow researchers to holistically understand the studied phenomenon by immersing oneself in the field and experiencing the research setting, this research approach seems essential for gaining an insight in customer experiences in actual retail environments (Denzin & Lincoln, 2005; Healy et al., 2007). Following Denzin (1989), we chose to apply the ethnographic method of subjective personal introspection (SPI) (Holbrook, 1986b; Gould, 1995). This method allows the researcher to be actively involved as 'research participant'. Patterson et al. (2008, p.31) describe it as the '*methodological doppelganger*' of customer experiences.

In SPI, which is also known in literature as 'auto-ethnography' (Ellis, 2008) or 'researcher introspection' (Wallendorf & Brucks, 1993), the researcher engages in a sort of participant observation of his or her own customer experiences, experienced in a certain context, and the meanings and emotions they evoke (Shankar, 2000; Shankar et al., 2001; Holbrook, 1995, 2006). Applying SPI can be particularly relevant in the early, exploratory stages of a qualitative, interpretive research process (Shankar, 2000), as it allows an enhancement of the body of knowledge. As a methodological approach, SPI has already been used to study consumer behavior (e.g., Gould, 1995; Shankar, 2000; Holbrook, 1986b; 2005).

As originally conceived, SPI focuses on the production of narrative accounts, which clarify the involved researcher's experiences. The production of these 'essays' requires input of the author's memories — personal memoirs that are possibly

sensitive to mental lapses. To overcome these issues, the support of relevant historical material, such as for instance field notes and photographs can be highly relevant (Holbrook, 2005).

Sample of stores

After having chosen to study customer experiences with the help of subjective personal introspection, twenty-three retail environments, located in three important shopping cities in the North part of Belgium (i.e. Flanders) were selected as examples of stores wherein the authors would immerse themselves in order to study their own customer experiences. The sample of stores to be visited in these cities was comprised after consulting two Belgian interior architects, who firstly both knew the Flemish retail landscape very well, and secondly, respectively had 30 years and 10 years of experience in the field of retail design. The stores to be visited thus were planned in advance. The sample of stores comprised different kinds of retail environments, ranging from interior design oriented stores, shoe and fashion stores, to general and specialist food stores. Figures 2 and 3 give an insight into a selection of the visited retail environments.

Figure 2. A selection of the visited retail environments (Xandres, Ghent)

Figure 3. A selection of the visited retail environments (Fish & Chips, Antwerp)

By choosing to study customer experiences in a very diverse sample of retail environments, we aimed to gain an insight into a broad range of customer experiences. Both authors visited the sample of stores separately, whereby the authors' respective cultural backgrounds were taken into account (the first author is from Belgium, the second from Mexico). Stores were visited during standard opening hours (i.e., between 9am and 6pm). The store visits of the first author each lasted between ten to fifteen minutes; those of the second author, approximately twenty minutes. During the store visits, both authors consciously avoided to present themselves as researchers to the store personnel. In that way, they functioned as 'instrument / subject' (Rod, 2006), while immersing themselves in the environment in relatively the same way as any other customer does.

Procedure

In all visits to retail environments, the Experience Web, discussed in the first section of this paper, functioned as a guide to help us rigorously document and explore our proper subjective experiences. While visiting the stores comprising the sample, the authors made multiple photographs in and outside the store to log elements that they valued to be important. In some stores, retailers were not eager to let the authors photograph their store; in these cases however, field notes mostly were allowed, which proved their value afterwards.

At the end of each day, filled with store visits, the authors' personal customer experiences were documented and studied for the first time via the collected field notes and photographs. Where necessary, they added some short remarks in their original field notes. In the days immediately following the store visits, the authors started writing narrative accounts on each store visit.

Due to the fact that both researchers had different backgrounds from where to 'start from', and given their cultural differences, it was expected they could have valued differently their experiences.

Data analyses

Ethnographic analyses typically work 'bottom up'; researchers start with studying the collected research data, aiming to look for patterns of thought (Riemer, 2008). Consequently, the starting-point for reflecting on the authors' customer experiences was the reading and the multiple re-reading of the narrative accounts, which they produced after having visited the sample stores. Next, and in line with what experienced ethnographic researchers advise to do when analysing the collected research data (Denzin & Lincoln, 1998; Fetterman, 2008; Riemer, 2008), we considered the possibility of organizing the stores into groups or categories that made sense to us. By iteratively studying the collected material (Fetterman, 2008), while taking the Experience Web into account, we discovered that the stores could be meaningfully organized into groups. In what follows, we firstly discuss the research results of the Belgian researcher (first author). Next, we elaborate on

the results of the study of the Mexican researcher (second author). We conclude this section with a discussion of the cross-cultural results.

Research results

Study 1. The Belgian lens

The five groups, which the first author was able to discriminate, differ in their attention for each of the terms of the Experience Web. In her narrative accounts, this author formulated five groups ranging from ‘stores that trigger a high level of experience’ to ‘stores that trigger a low level of experience’. In what follows, we shortly elaborate on her findings.

The *first group* of retail stores, mostly in the shoes and fashion segment, included six stores. These stores very obviously tried to trigger a high level of experience in the store environment. The message the retailer wants to communicate with its brand clearly is being translated into the retail store’s design. Most of the stores in this group sell rather expensive products (for instance designer clothing and shoes), so one could almost expect that the store’s retail design is in line with the products these stores are offering. The *second group* of stores that the first author was able to discriminate comprised twelve stores (the majority of the stores visited by the first author). The retail stores in this group are very diverse, ranging from a clothing store, to a design and accessories store, and a food store. These stores clearly try to trigger customer experiences by the way the store is designed, but according to the first author’s experiences, their efforts seem not to be as pronounced as was the case for the stores in the first group. The *third group* included three stores, consisting mostly of non-food stores. The stores comprising this group were mostly so-called ‘roll-out stores’, a term used to describe the reproduction of a certain retail concept into different store locations (Mesher, 2010). When designers work out concepts for ‘roll-out’ stores, the choices they can and need to make in the design process almost certainly will be influenced by working in the framework of this particular retail typology. The designers of the sample of stores the first author visited still tried to trigger experience with their store’s design, but the first author’s experiences generally were less pronounced than in the stores, belonging to the first and second group, described here above. The store, comprising the *fourth group*, is a store which, according to the first author’s subjective experiences, had potential for triggering customer experiences, but which did not really succeed in this mission. Again, we would like to stress that the results of this first study were based on the first author’s narrative accounts, which documented her subjective customer experiences and which inevitably have been influenced by her background and the feelings and emotions she experienced while visiting the sample of store environments. The store in the *fifth group* was a so-called discount store. For these types of stores, price is an important differentiation parameter (Mesher, 2010). As a consequence, the retail design of these stores is mostly homogeneous and relatively simple, as it needs to reflect the cheapness of the product offerings.

Study 2. The Mexican lens

Analyzing the results of study 2 results in the discrimination of six groups. The second author grouped the stores that the sample comprised while looking for overarching ‘labels’. According to her lens of looking at her data, the *first group* composed seven stores, which had in common ‘exclusivity’ in their interior design and also in their products. They offered clothes, shoes and accessories. Their prices were high, and their stores had a very stylish design on the interiors and finishings. The materials which they used were elegant and the experience which they offered made customers feel very ‘high class ambient’, worth paying a high sum of money. The *second group* was composed by five stores, which had in common ‘harmony’ in their design. They offered a specialized assortment of items (ranging from books to furniture and glasses), and there was a professional consultation provided by the staff. The retail design of these stores was attractive, pleasant and harmonious; it truly was related to the products the stores sold. The products these stores offered were of good quality and their prices ranged from medium to high. The *third group* was composed by only one store. The second author decided to make a separate group here, because it is quite different in nature from the rest of the stores comprising the sample. All products the store offers are discount items: they are of common use and quite cheap. The interiors have priorities, such as to highlight the products and prices, and the colors the store uses truly call for the attention of the customer. Two stores, which had in common the ‘authenticity’, compose the fourth group: they preserved the original, authentic building for the store, which truly makes these stores different from the other ones comprising the sample. The *fifth group* is composed by three stores, which had in common a ‘multisensory’ profile. Being inside these stores, people tend to have a truly hedonic experience, stimulated by different elements, some tangible elements, and others originating in the general store’s atmosphere. These stores want the customer to feel relaxed, free to try things, and dissolve the barriers between customers and products. The products they offer are gastronomic or relating to body care. The *sixth group* is composed by five stores, which had in common ‘originality’ and a free style in the way the products and the store are composed. Being inside these locations, it may cost customers some time to truly understand the store because the products they offer are various. In one store belonging to this group, the author also experienced different atmospheres.

Discussion of research results

Applying SPI has allowed us to uncover the subjective meanings, which the authors attributed to their personal customer experiences in twenty-three retail environments located in different shopping cities in Belgium. The difference in research results originating in a study of the same sample of stores illustrates firstly, the importance of applying a *holistic* research attitude when trying to understand how people experience a certain environment, and, secondly, the role of *cross-cultural aspects* in this respect.

With regards to the application of a *holistic research attitude*, we need to take into account that in designed environments, multiple factors interact and influence customer experiences. An illustration hereof relates to the fact that the stores comprising the different groups that the authors were able to discriminate were not equally spread over the different groups for the two authors. The stores that the Latin American researcher for instance grouped together under the label 'multisensory' were spread over three different groups in the analyses of the Belgian researcher. Although both researchers studied the same sample of stores, their experiences in these stores were different. This issue comes close to the second argument, which we discussed here above; that is, the role of *cross-cultural aspects*. Due to *cross-cultural aspects*, the end results of both researchers studying the same sample in stores are quite different: the Belgian researcher ended up with five groups of stores, while the Mexican researcher formulated six groups. The Belgian researcher took the subjective interpretation and translation of the Experience Web into retail practice as a starting-point for the analyses, whereas the Mexican researcher looked for a common factor in her narratives. While doing so, she ended up with six groups of stores.

CONCLUSION

Despite the currently shared positive connotation of customer experience in retail practice, there appears to be a lack of a clear conceptualization and empirical support. Recently, the Experience Web has been presented as a holistic framework for conceptualizing customer experiences (Petermans et al., 2013). In this paper, we opted to use an ethnographic research method to study customer experience in retail practice: SPI. This method allows a researcher to holistically understand the central research topic by immersing oneself in the field and experiencing the studied setting for oneself.

As the discussion of the research results has indicated, both authors are convinced that all commercial interiors integrate some degree of 'experience' into the retail design of their stores. However, the concrete translation and interpretation of the aspects of the Experience Web seems to differ. Cross-cultural issues certainly are an important parameter in this respect.

Although SPI already has been used in consumer behavior research in the past (Gould, 1995; Shankar, 2000; Holbrook, 1986b; 2005), there also are opponents of this research method (e.g., Wallendorf & Brucks, 1993; Woodside, 2004; 2006). They have criticized SPI for being value-laden and biased (Denzin & Lincoln, 1998). We agree that SPI undoubtedly is value-laden, but by explicating our proper experiences, we are able to question ourselves and our experiences far more critically than we would do with those of others (Shankar, 2000). Concerning the remark of research bias, the introspective data we collected in retail practice almost certainly will have been influenced by the reading we did prior to applying SPI in retail practice. However, because we were aware of this typical feature of qualitative inquiries, we used the knowledge from our

review of literature to inspire us in our introspective analyses. SPI furthermore has been criticized because of its relying on one's own subjective experiences as research data, without applying other research methods (Woodside, 2004; 2006). In response to this critique, we share the opinions of Gould (2004) and Shankar (2000) who indicated that there is no better place to start to study experiences than by examining our own. Indeed, SPI is a valuable method in the first, exploratory stages of a planned research program of different phases. This is also the way in which we used it.

This article focused on cross-culturally studying customer experiences by introspectively studying retail environments in different Belgian shopping cities. Further research needs to broaden our first exploratory cross-cultural perspectives. For instance, it seems worthwhile to cross-culturally study customer experiences in other geographic regions. In addition, it seems valuable to study in-depth experiences in a limited number of stores, whereby more cross-cultural participants and relevant stakeholders can be involved in the process. In the 2013 publication, for instance, we studied the perspectives of retailers, designers, and ordinary actual customers with regards to the Experience Web. It seems worthwhile for future cross-cultural research with the Web to follow a similar approach. Likewise, it seems particularly interesting to find out if our conceptualization of customer experiences — the Experience Web — is also applicable, and a valuable 'evaluation tool' in experiential spaces other than retail environments, such as hotels, care facilities etcetera.

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CAPTURING CONFLICT EXPERIENCES FIVE METHODS FOR IDENTIFYING INTRAPERSONAL CONCERN CONFLICTS

Deger Ozkaramanli, Elif Özcan, Pieter M. A. Desmet
Delft University of Technology
✉ d.ozkaramanli@tudelft.nl, e.ozcan@tudelft.nl, p.m.a.desmet@tudelft.nl

ABSTRACT

This paper starts from the proposition that concern conflicts can be powerful starting points for user-centered design processes. Our focus is on the challenge to identify conflicting concerns that are both inspiring and relevant in the context of use, or in the user's general context of life. First, three main ingredients of concern conflict experiences are introduced: choices, goals, and emotions. We propose that any of these ingredients can be used as an entry point to access concern conflict experiences. Next, five research methods are suggested that can be used to identify relevant and inspiring concern conflicts; three methods that are user-centered, and two that are designer-centered. We describe these methods using illustrative research contexts with the intention to inform and inspire suitable research protocols when designers are actively seeking concern conflicts.

KEYWORDS: *design, concern, conflict, tool, method*

INTRODUCTION

What do you do when your alarm clock goes off in the morning? Do you immediately jump out of bed or do you keep snoozing your clock at the risk of being late for work? This is the first concern conflict that many of us experience in a typical day: we may want to wake up early (concern for timeliness), which conflicts with wanting to relax in bed for as long as possible (concern for comfort). Many daily decisions involve such concern conflicts. For example, we may want to spend quality time with our loved ones (concern for belonging), yet we may also want to work extra hours to ensure a successful career (concern for professional success). We may decide to skip our gym-night to go to the movies (concern for fun), and yet, wish we would have a fine-looking body like the movie stars we admire (concern for beauty). These concern conflicts are 'the rule in everyday life rather than the exception' (Frijda, 2010, p.70). Ignoring them when designing products would be like ignoring a crucial part of what makes users human. In this paper, we propose that concern conflicts can, in fact, be an inspiring starting point for user-centered design, and suggest that designers can actively seek for —and design with— concern conflicts to create user-relevant products and services.

An example of a conflict-inspired design is the 'Uniekies Game' (Figure one), which was designed by Janine Innemee with the goal of helping able-bodied children to empathize with disabled children in the context of social play.¹ In this case, the designer found that able-bodied children were ambivalent towards including disabled children in play activities. Playing with disabled children slowed down the game leading to boredom (concern for fun); however, completely excluding them caused able-bodied children to feel guilty (concern for unity). The game addresses this concern conflict by introducing disabled children as heroes with special powers who are to be admired. Able-bodied children can also become heroes by dressing up in special suits and training their powers. For example, Bumper (Figure one) symbolizes a child in a wheelchair who cannot run, but has the unique power of quickly clearing off the play-path for his followers. When playing the game, an able bodied child can wear a balloon-suit to experience the challenges of being in a wheelchair in a fun way. As a result, the Uniekies Game creates a play context that enables challenging solidarity, and thus, fulfills conflicting concerns simultaneously.

¹ The Uniekies Game was the outcome of Innemee's graduation project at the faculty of Industrial Design Engineering, Delft University of Technology, supervised by the first author and Dr. Mathieu Gielen.

Figure 1. Uniekies game (Innemeer, 2014); reprinted with permission.

Concern conflicts arise in every design context without exception; people have an endless number of concerns governing their daily interactions that often conflict with each other. In the Uniekies Game project, the designer collected many concerns, which were either congruent or conflicting. She could have taken any of these concerns as the leading theme for designing something that appeals to the children. For example, the concern for challenge can be the basis for conceptualizing new and exciting challenges; however, these concepts may exclude disabled children. Alternatively, the concern for inclusion can be the basis for designing games that integrate disabled children into play; however, these concepts may lack the challenge for able-bodied children. The point here is that, in both directions, the resulting designs will both generate positive and negative experiences. Therefore, we propose that focusing on the tension between the concerns, rather than on specific concerns in isolation, can lead to solutions that solve this emotional duality.

In line with this focus, the purpose of this paper is to assist designers in identifying relevant and inspiring concern conflicts, as input for their design process. The inspiring nature of using concern conflicts in design activities has been shown in several studies. Tromp et al. (2011) adopted an interpersonal approach to conflict-driven design and utilized the concept in motivating socially responsible behavior (e.g. reducing litter in public environments). Ozkaramanli et al. (2012) focused specifically on intrapersonal conflicts between long-term and short-term concerns; and provided multiple design directions to handle such conflicts. In addition, a theoretical framework that supports our understanding of concern conflicts has been published (Ozkaramanli & Desmet, 2012).

An important challenge in this approach is that it requires identifying users' experiences of concern conflicts that are relevant to the user and inspiring to the designer. To facilitate the activity of formulating concern sets, Desmet (2008) proposed a matrix with nine distinct sources of product emotion. Each source represents a particular concern type. Although this matrix supports designers in formulating a broad set of user concerns, it does not offer assistance in prioritizing between concerns. Moreover, the matrix represents isolated concerns without supporting designers in identifying promising or inspiring concern conflicts. To support designers in this challenge, this paper introduces research tools that can be of use in identifying

concern conflicts. First, the concept of concern is discussed. Next, the three main ingredients of concern conflict experiences are proposed, each of which can be used as an entry point to access concern conflicts. Finally, five research methods are introduced and discussed, which are either user-centered or designer-centered. The intention of introducing these methods is to inform and inspire suitable research protocols for those who want to identify and define usable concern conflicts.

CONFLICTING CONCERNS

Concern is a collective term that refers to people's goals and motives (see Frijda, 1988). Concerns play a key role in our emotions: we get emotional about events that are perceived as being relevant for one or more of our concerns (Arnold, 1960). When the event matches our concern, we experience a positive emotion, and when there is a mismatch, we experience a negative emotion. Hence, concerns can play an important role in emotion-driven design: one potent way to design for emotion is to design for concerns. Considering that people have numerous concerns in their daily interactions, an important question is which of these concerns are relevant and inspiring as input for user-centered design processes. In this paper, we focus on intrapersonal concern conflicts as powerful starting points for user-centered design. For this, we use a phenomenological perspective to discuss the 'lived experience' of concern conflicts (i.e. conflict experiences). In this perspective, *concerns* (or goals) are one of the three main ingredients of conflict experiences (Ozkaramanli et al., 2012). The other two ingredients are *choices* and *emotions* (Ozkaramanli et al., 2012). To illustrate the three ingredients, we will use the following anecdote:

Imagine Jane, who has to get up early for a Skype meeting at 7 AM; and because she woke up a bit late, she needs to rush her morning routine. In her kitchen, she has to decide on what her morning drink will be. For a moment she hesitates: should she prepare herself a cup of tea or a cup of coffee? On the one hand, she prefers coffee because it will keep her energized during her morning meeting (concern for competence). On the other hand, she prefers tea because it takes less time to prepare than preparing coffee does, which assures her that she will not be late for the meeting (concern for timeliness).

(1) Choices

Jane's moment of indecision or hesitation between two choices is an essential ingredient of all conflict experiences (see Figure two): She can either choose 'A' (prepare tea) or choose 'B' (prepare coffee). Conflict experiences always involve such a decision, in which both choices (A and B) come with 'gains and losses', because they match with one concern and conflict with another concern. Note that not every decision turns into a conflict. Conflict experiences are triggered only when one becomes aware that each choice will lead to gains and losses that are relevant for one's concerns in varying degrees. Consequently, the person starts deliberating the consequences of each choice.

(2) Goals

Jane's dilemma is fuelled by her goals to be competent and punctual. It is important to note that this conflict experience is context-driven: the two goals do not conflict as such because, in principle, Jane can be competent and punctual at the same time. In this specific context, however, the two goals are conflicting. In addition, it is not the (anticipated) events as *such* (e.g. being late and energized with coffee, or being on time and still sleepy with tea) that trigger the conflict experience. Instead, the conflict experience is triggered by the *evaluation* of these events in terms of their consequences for one's wellbeing, for which our goals serve as points of reference (see Figure three).

(3) Emotions

In her moment of hesitation, Jane experienced mixed emotions (see Figure four). If she chooses tea, she may feel confident because she knows she will not be late for the meeting. Yet, she may feel regret because she knows she will not have the energy to contribute much to the meeting. If she chooses coffee, she may feel proud because she knows she will be sharp in the meeting. Yet, she may anticipate feeling guilty due to being late. Emotions bring the experiential quality to conflict experiences. If there is no emotion, there would be no concern at stake, and thus, no conflict would be experienced. These emotions are all anticipated emotions in nature, i.e., they are emotions experienced in response to potential future outcomes (see Perugini & Bagozzi, 2001). Emotions experienced in the moment of decision-making may, for example, be doubt, reluctance, hope, fear or worry, which are evoked in response to indecision instead of potential outcomes.

The three ingredients of conflict experiences enable us to summarize Jane's concern conflict in Figure four. Even though the specific choices, goals, and emotions are different for each conflict, it should be possible to determine these three ingredients in every experienced conflict. You may now think that one would not invest so much cognitive and emotional effort in making simple decisions such as preparing tea or preparing coffee; however, our brains do. According to recent research, goal conflicts can occur outside of conscious awareness (Kleiman & Hassin, 2011). This is because people have many goals that are potentially conflicting, while our mental resources are too limited to resolve all goal conflicts within our conscious awareness (Kleiman & Hassin, 2011). Therefore, we often experience manifestations of goal conflicts such as *behavioral variability, increased decision time, and emotional arousal* (Kleiman & Hassin, 2011). These manifestations might be linked to the ingredients of conflict experiences. In essence, behavioral

variability corresponds to indecision evoked by two choices, while increased decision time corresponds to weighing out potential gains and losses with respect to goals, and emotional arousal corresponds to mixed emotions. These three manifestations can act as 'cues' or 'symptoms' for designers when diagnosing the presence of a goal conflict in specific situations.

Figure 2. Choices involved in the conflict experience.

Figure 3. Choices and goals involved in the conflict experience.

Figure 4. Choices, goals, and emotions involved in the conflict experience.

- From a motivational perspective, the three types of concerns (goals, standards, attitudes) can be linked to high-order goals such as those provided by Ford (1992). Thus, the words 'concern' and 'goal' can be used interchangeably in the context of conflict experiences.

METHODS FOR IDENTIFYING CONCERN CONFLICTS

To use concern conflicts as input for their process, designers need to actively seek concern conflicts in the research context they intend to design for. We propose that any of the three main ingredients (choices, goals, or emotions) can be used as an entry point for probing conflict experiences. However, different research contexts may require using different entry points. A complication is that people simply do not always have conscious access to their concerns (see Wilson, 2002). This task becomes much more challenging in the case of conflict experiences, because people tend to ignore or deny conflicting thoughts as a way of maintaining consistency in attitudes or behavior (see Festinger, 1957; Bem, 1967). In this section, we suggest five qualitative research methods that can help access relevant and inspiring concern conflicts. The suggested methods can be divided into two categories:

- (1) *User-centered methods* that involve users as research participants in data collection: Emotion Capture Card (ECC) procedure, experience booklets, and phenomenological interviewing.
- (2) *Designer-centered methods* that rely on the knowledge and judgments of the design team and possibly other experts: introspection and co-exploration.

The suggested methods are exemplified using illustrative research contexts with the intention to inform and inspire suitable research protocols for the design brief at hand.

User-centered research methods

We propose three user-centered research methods for accessing concern conflicts. *Emotion Capture Card* procedure (ECC) originates from design research and has been previously applied by Ozkaramanli et al. (2013). *Experience booklets* and *phenomenological interviewing* are widely used in psychology (see Moustakas, 1994), and their combination has been previously applied in design research (see Ozkaramanli et al., 2012; Fokkinga & Desmet, 2012).

Emotion capture card procedure

Frijda (1988) formulated the ‘law of concern’, which states that every emotion hides a concern. In line with this law, an individual’s emotions can be considered as reliable entry points to their concerns. Imagine, for example, a friend who is disappointed after watching Eastwood’s movie *Million Dollar Baby*. In the after-movie conversation, you may discover that the underlying concern that created your friend’s disappointment was a ‘concern for happy endings’. Emotion capture cards are based on this law of concern.

Consider a design brief in which the context of design or the product to be designed is already specified in the brief, such as: designing a coffee-machine that enhances the morning experience of working mothers. In this case, it might be fruitful to focus research efforts on the given context by implementing

the Emotion Capture Card (ECC) procedure (see Ozkaramanli et al., 2013). ECC procedure follows three main stages: (1) capturing emotions, (2) distilling concerns, and (3) formulating concern conflicts.

In the first stage, the research team captures emotions (both positive and negative) through observing a working mother (i.e., research participant) in a relatively unobtrusive way as she goes through an activity, while occasionally probing her for emotions. The participant can either report emotions as they arise, or researchers can prompt for an emotion when they observe an emotional event.

In the second stage, the research team interviews the participant using a laddering-type technique to deepen the understanding of concerns underlying emotions (see Reynolds & Gutman, 1988). For example, if the mother gets angry with her kid for not finishing her breakfast, she can be probed to specify the personal reasoning underlying this emotion using a laddering technique (e.g. Researcher: *why were you angry?* Participant: *because, I want my children to have enough energy for school*). Both positive and negative emotions can be reliable entry points for concerns. In addition, mixed emotions can be valuable entry points for capturing concern conflicts, since, based on the ‘law of concern’ (Frijda, 1988), mixed emotions can guard multiple concerns. The emotion capture card shown in Figure five facilitates the first two stages of the ECC procedure.

In the third stage, the research team forms an overview of participants’ concerns and focuses on relationships among these concerns to formulate potential concern conflicts (see Ozkaramanli et al., 2013). For example, some of the concerns in the above example might be ‘being a good mother’, ‘maintaining order in the kitchen’, ‘having me-time’, and ‘being a responsible employee’. Through comparing and contrasting these concerns, the research team can formulate potential concern conflicts. In this example, a concern conflict might occur between the concerns ‘being a good mother’ and ‘having me-time’: being a good mother requires the mother to invest time in taking care of children in the morning, while she may also desire a quiet moment for herself.

Experience booklets and phenomenological interviewing

Consider a design brief in which the context of design and product to be designed are open to interpretation, such as: improving the university campus environment to enhance academic success. In this case, the design team might be able to formulate suitable design contexts, such as lecture rooms or study rituals, and actively seek conflict experiences in these contexts using ECC procedure. Alternatively, the design team might start with researching students’ concerns and concern conflicts in a holistic manner, for example, by investigating students’ academic experiences across multiple contexts. For the second alternative, experience booklets in combination with phenomenological interviewing might be a more efficient approach than applying ECC procedure for multiple times in multiple contexts.

Experience booklets provide a medium for participants to record their conflict experiences by answering a number of questions designed to probe these experiences. Here, the goal is to bring conflict experiences into awareness and to collect inspiring concern conflicts (see Ozkaramanli et al., 2012). Similar to cultural probes (Gaver et al., 1999), experience booklets target inspirational quality rather than quantity in participants' responses. However, experience booklets are different than cultural probes or sensitizing booklets (Sleeswijk Visser et al., 2005), since they target experiences related to a specific phenomenon rather than information on general characteristics of users and their context. Figure six and Figure seven show possible questions that students might be asked in an experience booklet designed for the given research context.

Figure 5. An example of a filled emotion capture card (the white section is used to take notes during observations, and the gray section is completed after the laddering interview).

The question in the booklet example in Figure six uses the well-known metaphor of an angel 'should-self' fighting against an evil 'want-self' to probe for conflict experiences between long-term goals and short-term pleasures (Mikman et al., 2008). This question uses choices (instead of goals or emotions), as an entry point to the conflict experience, where the choices may, for example, be 'I should study for my exam' versus 'I want to play the guitar'. In Figure seven, the question uses goals as an entry point (instead of choices or emotions) to probe conflict experiences. In this question, the focus is on the interference (i.e. conflict) among goals, where pursuing an academic goal interferes with the pursuit of another important goal due to limited resources such as time, energy, or money (Riediger & Freund, 2004).

Phenomenological interviewing can be facilitated by using the responses given in the experience booklet as input (see Ozkaramanli et al., 2012; Fokkinga & Desmet, 2012). According to Moustakas (1994), phenomenological interviews can be conducted in an informal, open, and interactive way, and in a setting that is natural to the participant. The fundamental question that needs to be answered in the phenomenological interview is 'What is it like to experience this specific phenomenon?' (Englander, 2012). For conflict experiences, the interviewer and the participant can go through the responses given in the experience booklet and discuss them in greater depth, for example by collecting information on choices, goals, and emotions involved in these experiences (see Ozkaramanli et al., 2012).

Designer-centered research methods

We propose two designer-centered methods for accessing concern conflicts: introspection for exploring concern conflicts through designer's own conflict experiences; and co-explo-

Figure 6. Booklet page that asks about choices of a 'should-self' versus a 'want-self'.

Figure 7. Booklet page that asks about an experience when pursuit of an academic goal interferes with the pursuit of another important goal due to limited resources such as time, energy, or money.

ration for exploring concern conflicts through collaboratively formulating insights in a team of designers and experts. Consider a design domain that has been widely researched such as: motivating sustainable eating habits by reducing red-meat consumption (see Ozkaramanli & Desmet, 2012). Sustainable eating is a broad design domain that hosts many controversies and opposing opinions. More importantly, much has been written on this topic, in academia and other fields, which can form reliable sources of information for the design team. Due to abundance of research material in this domain, it might be a plausible approach to involve members of the design team, and expert opinion to identify relevant and inspiring concern conflicts, instead of involving users.

Introspection

Introspection can be defined as ‘an ongoing process of tracking, experiencing, and reflecting on one’s own thoughts, mental images, feelings, sensations, and behaviors’ (Gould, 1995, p.1). Introspection might be particularly suited for investigating conflict experiences for two reasons: they are abundant in everyday life, and they are emotional (i.e. self-relevant) phenomena that can grab attention. Designers can use introspection by being mindful about and reflecting on situations in which they *themselves* experience the symptoms of conflict (i.e. behavioral variability, prolonged decision making, and emotional arousal), which might enhance designers’ understanding of the phenomenon through first-hand insights. For example, in the domain of sustainable eating, the designer might choose to systematically record moments of hesitation regarding selection, preparation, and consumption of food. Here, introspective thought exercises suggested by Gould (2012) can help focus designers’ awareness on their mental processes.

It is important to note that introspection is considered a controversial method in consumer research (Gould, 1995; Gould,

2013), and thus, understanding its contribution to designing requires future research. However, using this method in combination with user-centered research methods might facilitate mediation between designers’ personal insights and the insights obtained from future users.

Co-exploration

We propose co-exploration as a work-in-progress procedure that can be used by designers and experts to collaboratively formulate possible concern conflicts in a specific design domain. We suggest that the proposed tool shown in Figure eight can facilitate this collaboration. The tool is composed of an infographic of several conflict experiences in different contexts, and a set of goal cards inspired by the goal taxonomy of Ford (1992). The tool works as a two-step creativity tool typically used in brainstorming sessions. In the first step, the research team explores the infographic to acquire an understanding of conflict experiences. Next, each team member picks a concern card and tries to formulate a concern conflict by pairing this card with the card of another team member using free association. Imagine that a member of the design team picked the card of ‘tranquility’ while another member picked the card of ‘mastery’ (see Figure eight). By pairing these two cards, the team can brainstorm about possible conflict experiences that involve these two specific concerns and are relevant for the design brief at hand. A possible concern conflict between ‘tranquility’ and ‘mastery’ in the domain of sustainable eating may be summarized in the following narrative: ‘*I want to master the art of cooking by combining different vegetables with spices; however, when I get out of work, I am usually too tired to bother with cleaning, chopping and cooking vegetables – it is a lot easier to grill a piece of steak and eat it with some mashed potatoes*’. Following this formulation, the design team can discuss emotions and choices involved in this specific con-

Figure 8. Pairing example goal cards for formulating concern conflicts by free association (goal definitions are adopted from Ford (1992)).

flict experience. The design team can repeat this exercise until designers and experts agree upon a relevant and inspiring set of concern conflicts.

DISCUSSION

Conflict experience is a rich, everyday phenomenon that can be an inspiring starting point for user-centered design. This paper conceptualized concern conflicts as an experience that involves three main ingredients, namely choices, goals, and emotions. Additionally, we suggested five qualitative research methods that might help designers in identifying concern conflicts. In explaining the methods, we discussed three research contexts that differed from each other in the way that they specified the intended design context. The selection of these research contexts were random yet relevant for illustrating the implementation of the proposed research methods. It is possible to swap the research methods between the illustrated research contexts, or even to use them in combination. Here, it is up to the design team to select the most suitable research methods based on the qualities of the research context, and the goals and the resources of the design team.

We made a distinction between user-centered and designer-centered research methods. User-centered methods (ECC procedure, experience booklets, and phenomenological interviewing) are empirical methods that yield detailed insights into the lived experience of conflicts, as experienced by potential users (see Ozkaramanli & Desmet, 2012; Ozkaramanli et al., 2013). Therefore, they might be valuable research methods if the design team feels that involving users will lead to deeper insights on conflict experiences in a given domain. Designer-centered methods (introspection and co-exploration) rely on the knowledge and judgments of the design team instead of those of users. Introspection can deliver rich insights on specific experiences (Gould, 2013); however, the insights are limited to the experiences of one person, and thus, may not be generalizable to all potential users. Co-exploration might deliver reliable insights based on expert opinion; however, it might not yield a rich understanding of conflict experiences in terms of choices and emotions involved. There are emerging perspectives in design research that support designers in using their own experiences when designing or evaluating products, such as autobiographical design (see Neustaedter & Sengers, 2012), designer experience (see Nieminen et al., 2011) and immersion (see Jordan, 2000). Additionally, it could be a valuable approach to combine (i.e. to triangulate) user-centered and designer-centered research methods to ensure identification of relevant and inspiring concern conflicts.

Design teams can access concern conflicts either directly or indirectly. When using the ECC procedure, design teams formulate concern conflicts by comparing and contrasting users' concerns captured in a specific context by using emotions as an entry point. This is an indirect way of identifying concern conflicts, and the findings need to be evaluated either by users or by experts to ensure that the design team has a relevant set

of concern conflicts. Alternatively, design teams can identify concern conflicts by asking questions directly about the conflict experiences. For this, design teams can formulate questions such as those in Figure six and Figure seven, or they can be observant about the symptoms of conflict experiences, (i.e. behavioral variability, increased decision time, and emotional arousal) when observing users or when using introspection.

Following identification of concern conflicts, designers will need to determine which concern conflicts they would like to focus on when designing. From users' perspective, the intensity of emotions experienced in the conflict experience might indicate whether the concern conflict is worthy of designing. The stronger the emotions, the more important the concerns at stake (Frijda, 1988), indicating a strong concern conflict. Additionally, repetitive conflict experiences might be worthy of designing, since they indicate that users might need support in dealing with these concern conflicts (see Ozkaramanli et al., 2012). From designers' perspective, we suggest that concern conflicts need to be formulated at an appropriate abstraction level that supports creativity while maintaining relevance for potential users: concern conflicts that are too abstract and general (e.g. responsibility versus competence), or concern conflicts that are too concrete and context-specific (e.g. preparing tea versus preparing coffee), might hinder creativity.

Limitations and future research

The proposed research methods are intended as a possible tool-set that might help in identifying relevant and inspiring concern conflicts. These methods need further reflection and evaluation before establishing their effectiveness in accessing concern conflicts, and new methods may be added to the list following further research. Additionally, translation of research goals into simple and concise questions, understandable by users, can be a challenging task. Further research is needed to eliminate semantic issues while talking with users about abstract concepts, such as emotions, concerns, and concern conflicts, to enhance the effectiveness of user-centered methods. Most importantly, identifying concern conflicts takes designers only half way through the design process. As a result, further research is needed to address the following questions: 'what are possible criteria for determining the most inspiring concern conflicts?' and 'what are the design strategies that can form viable starting points for designing with concern conflicts?' Our future work will focus on answering these questions.

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EMOTIONAL DESIGN THROUGH MEASUREMENT OF PSYCHOPHYSIOLOGICAL AND BEHAVIORAL PARAMETERS: TAKING STEPS TOWARDS NEURODESIGN

Noé Gonzalez Monestina, Daniel Puente Berdasco, María Begoña Jorda Albiñana, Teresa Magal Royo
Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingeniería del Diseño, Universidad Politécnica de Valencia
✉ nogonmo@alumni.upv.es; dapueber@etsid.upv.es; bego@mag.upv.es; tmagal@degi.upv.es

ABSTRACT

There are a number of unknowns regarding conventional Emotional Design methodologies, especially in terms of the feedback from target users. Grey areas include questions such as: why are these methodologies so trusting of the user's response? Does the user really understand what is being asked of them? How do such methodologies consider the external factors that condition the emotional state of the individual, and therefore their answer? Is a subjective analysis of the emotion resulting from the cognitive interpretation of a stimulus sufficient? If it is indeed possible to measure the physiological reflex of an emotion, why is this parameter rarely considered as a viable option?

The main objective of this investigation is to respond to these questions, thus making the possibility of project development via emotional design more accessible. This can be achieved by leveraging the objectivity of the physiological register through the use of appropriate technology, and by fine-tuning the technical specifications and product design parameters which relate to the end-user's various needs, in terms of product functionality, usability and the user's emotional involvement.

KEYWORDS: *neurodesign, biofeedback, neuroscience, psychophysiology, brain, neuromarketing*

INTRODUCTION

Throughout history, cognition and emotion have been considered as being independent, even opposing, processes. The Greeks made the distinction between reason and passion, thus separating thoughts from feelings. Reason was considered the medium for thinking clearly by controlling our passions, which in turn were thought of as out-of-control emotions that blur our capacity for reasoning (Belmonte, 2007). During the 17th century Descartes lent weight to this idea and supported this distinction in his research. He considered that the mind was void of either **spatial extension** or physical content, two characteristics that would allow it to live when the body no longer existed. By discounting any of the physical properties of the mind, Descartes rendered the link between mind and body for the fulfillment of its supposed functions impossible. The mind-body conundrum has remained unsolved until the present day, recurring as a constant subject of debate in the fields

of psychology and philosophy. Even in the 20th century, and in spite of the evolution of the sciences of mind and brain, there were so many opposing approaches and methodologies that it was impossible to tackle the problem with any hope of reaching a solution (Damasio, 2011). It seems that finally in the last decade, thanks largely to the contributions of important scientists and neurologists such as Joseph LeDoux and Antonio Damasio, the close link between emotion and cognition has started to gain acceptance. Underlying the conscious components of both, it is clear that diverse, subconscious brain mechanisms interact to determine the conscious characteristics of thought and emotion.

Thanks to the work of these scientists, and the advances in the technological aspects of the devices used in their research, new advances in neuroscience have been made that allow us to recognize that cognition and emotion are unified and that they contribute jointly and equally to the control of thought and behavior (LeDoux, 1995).

Cognition includes aspects such as perception, memory, attention, or action, while *emotion* ranges from a person's subjective feelings to their body's physiological and physical reactions to stimulus.

THE STRUCTURE OF EMOTIONS

As with its theoretical conception, there is no general consensus on the structures that make up emotions. Some researchers use categories, others dimensions, some employ bipolar concepts, some **unipolar concepts**, some propose a simple structure, some a circumplex model, and still others a hierarchical model (Russell & Feldman, 1999).

For Russell, emotions cover too many types of event to be described in a unique scientific category, and it seems impossible to merge them together to form a unique structure. As an example, let us take the distinction between core-affective and prototypical emotional episodes. The former refers to the consciously accessible elementary processes of pleasure and activation, which are caused by multiple factors, and are always present. Its structure implies two bipolar dimensions. The latter corresponds to a complex process developed over time, consisting of a series of causally-connected components (for example, background, personal evaluation, physiological, affective and cognitive changes, behavioral responses, auto-categorization), but has a single perceived cause and is singular in nature. Its structure includes verbal categories, vertically organized in a confused hierarchy, and horizontally organized as part of a circumplex. This approach to the discrepancy between a structure based on categories and another based on dimensions was also discussed by Fijda y Mesquita (1998).

One of the main difficulties of the categorical structure is that the terms used to define the categories themselves in any given language are similar in other languages but not identical. To this, add the fact that each category is more a question of degrees than of absolute extremes, and the distinctions between these categories become blurred. Furthermore, these categories describe complex processes formed by a set of temporally-ordered and causally-related components.

The variability of the relationship between the components of an emotion and the ambiguity, from a semantic point of view, of the concepts of emotions therefore render named categories less adequate than the names given to their component emotions (or dimensions).

THEORIES OF EMOTIONS

As a consequence of the ambiguity in the definition, classification or structure of emotions, a great diversity of approaches has arisen, each derived from different theoretical models as a function of the emotional component that formed the basis of its interest.

The principal conceptual developments can be classified in a similar way to that of Plutchik (1980): evolutionist, cognitive,

behavioral, psychological, and neurological, although in this article we will cover only the last two.

Psychophysiological

The psychophysiological part of the idea proposed by James (James, 1884, quoted by Chóliz, 2005) considers that an emotion arises as a consequence of the interpretation of a determined physiological response produced by a definite event. According to the hypothesis of James-Lange, each emotional reaction could be identified through a determined and differentiated physiological pattern. This directional fractionation (Lacey, 1967, cited by Zhóliz, 2005) is characterized by the fact that an emotional response is either sympathetic or parasympathetic, favoring the appearance of differentiated response patterns for each affective reaction. Numerous studies along these lines have allowed the identification of variables such as heart rate, conductivity, or body temperature when faced with specific events. These results could be explained through the existence of psycho-biological programs specific to each emotion, which would facilitate our ability to adapt our behavior to a given situation. The various studies that have been performed have involved the monitoring of different systems including electrodermal response, gastrointestinal activity, cardiovascular activity, muscular activity, respiratory activity and, with the evolution of technology in the last few years, asymmetry in Electroencephalography when experiencing a range of emotions.

Neurological

Even though the James-Lange hypothesis established that the physiological base of emotions is located in visceral mechanisms, Cannon considered that the physiological base was in the thalamus and hypothalamus. The thalamus gives an emotional quality to the impulses that pass through it; an environmental stimulus acts on the receptors, which send that stimulus to the cortex via the thalamus. The cortex again stimulates the thalamus, which then acts according to predetermined patterns corresponding to specific forms of emotional expression. For Cannon, the activation of thalamic neurons acts as an activator of muscles and viscera, and sends feedback to the cerebral cortex, demonstrating that emotional experience and physical change occur almost simultaneously (Palmero, 1996). Ultimately, the Cannon-Bard activation theory argues that an emotion is a sign of an emergency situation, and motivates the organism to react and control that emotion.

Papez and McLean established the physiological base of emotions as residing in the limbic system. For both the authors, the hypothalamus and limbic system provide the biological substrate for an emotional experience. Papez speculated on the existence of specific brain areas dedicated to emotions. He considered that the hypothalamus was the sender and receiver of information to and from the limbic brain and that the hippocampus acted as coordinator or regulator between the hypothalamus and the cingulate cortex and the parahippocampal gyrus (Belmonte, 2007). The expression of emotions implies a hypothalamic control of visceral organs, while

feelings appear in the 'Papez circuit' (Palmero, 1996). In the end, the brain areas that form this circuit are related to the limbic system, as referred to by McLean (McLean, 1949, cited by Palermo, 1996). The main contribution from McLean was the consideration that the human encephalon is a system formed of three layers, colloquially known as the 'Reptilian complex', responsible for the automatic, instinctive behavior necessary for the organism's survival; the 'Paleomammalian complex', in charge of the conservation of both the species and individual; and the 'Neomammalian complex', necessary for the development of rational strategies and for verbal capacity.

Lindsley's 'activation theory' situates the physiological base of emotion in the reticulated formation of the brain stem, and accepts that the hypothalamus is the main area for the organization of emotional expression. Lindsley considers that the reticulated system must be activated in any significant expression of behavior. When a stimulus appears, sensory, visceral, and somatic impulses take the following course: arrival at and integration into the reticulated formation, followed by transmission to the hypothalamus and thalamus centers where they activate the cerebral cortex. This activation occurs concurrently to electro-cortical de-synchronization, giving rise to the possibility of finding a minimal level of activation in non-emotional situations, and the highest level of activation in situations of extreme emotional excitation (Palmero, 1996).

The relationship between emotion and activation is defined by the existence of a main process, wherein cortical, autonomous, and somatic systems are coordinated. This process would be responsible for the quality of the different affective reactions. As a consequence, prominent studies have been characterized by the selection of a particular physiological variable as an indicator of the activation level, in order to register its correlation to different emotional reactions.

Damasio (2011) proposes the following hypothesis about work on emotions: strictly speaking, an emotion such as happiness, sadness, shame or sympathy is a complex set of chemical and neuronal responses that form a distinctive pattern. A normal brain produces responses when it detects an Emotionally Competent Stimulus (ECS). This is the object or event whose presence, whether real or remembered, triggers the emotion. Such responses are automatic.

In every emotion, neuronal and chemical discharges occur that temporarily modify, in a specific way, our internal state, our visceral organs, and our musculo-skeletal systems. Everything that makes up a human being, from facial expressions to behavioral patterns, is established in this way. Damasio (2011) has established schematically that the trigger and execution of emotions happens as follows: firstly, the evaluation and definition of an ECS activates the areas of the cerebral cortex associated with the senses and those of a higher order; next, what Damasio refers to as the emotional 'trigger', or induction, occurs, which takes place in the cerebral amygdala. Subsequently, emotional execution occurs in the basal fore-brain, involving the hypothalamus and brain stem. Lastly, the emotional state is produced, causing a series of transitory changes in the internal condition.

FROM NEUROSCIENCE TO MARKETING: NEUROMARKETING

Neuroscience, 'the science of the brain', is defined by Kandel (2000) as a fusion of different disciplines, including molecular biology, electrophysiology, anatomy, embryology and developmental biology, cell biology, and behavioral biology. This fusion aims to contribute to the explanation of human behavior in terms of brain activity and how their environment, and even the behavior of other human beings, influence cells.

A pioneering example of the application of neuroscience to business can be seen in marketing, whose development has been based on knowledge gained from other disciplines such as psychology, sociology, economics, and anthropology. When advances in neuroscience and neuropsychology were incorporated, an extraordinary evolution took place, resulting in the creation of a new discipline known as neuromarketing (Braïdot, 2005).

Neuromarketing incorporates a range of resources based on the understanding of brain processes linked to sensory perception, information processing, memory, attention span, rationality, emotions, and mechanisms that interact during learning and decision making, allowing us to overcome potential errors caused by a lack of awareness of the related internal processes and the metaconscious.

According to Epstein (1994), people sense reality in at least two different ways: cognitively, which is considered to be analytical and rational, and affectively, which is considered to be intuitive and experiential. Recent studies have determined that up to 95% of our decision-making happens at the fringe of our consciousness. Our senses receive around eleven million bits of information every second, whilst the conscious brain can only process some forty bits per second. The subconscious, or the affective way of processing information, is some 200 times faster. This is due mainly to the fact that cognitive processes involve an automatic and simultaneous search of our experience database. In some ways, it is as if the brain searches in its memory database for related events, including possible combinations and consequences.

This means that the cerebral areas of rationality cannot work in isolation from the areas of biological-emotional regulation. The two systems communicate with one another and hence jointly affect our behavior.

The great challenge seems to lie in predicting the latent needs of users and what their behavior will be during their interaction with the product or service, so as to contribute to a more positive user experience (Khalid, M.H., 2006).

One example of Neuromarketing can be found in the work of Lindstrom (2008), who carried out various studies employing magnetic resonance to record the majority of their results. One of the most surprising insights they gained into the relationship between our brain and emotions concerns the warnings found on tobacco and cigarette packaging. From a rational perspective, such warnings should, in principle, act as a deterrent and

reduce tobacco consumption among smokers. In reality however, their effect is quite the opposite; they cause an activation of the ACCUMBENS centre of the brain, known as the 'point of anxiousness', which in turn increases the desire of the smoker to light up a cigarette. Nevertheless, from the responses given in a related questionnaire, the majority of these tobacco users felt that these warnings did indeed act as a deterrent. Such a response illustrates the fact that focusing solely on subjective aspects of our emotions can introduce a source of error in the interpretation of a study's results, a fact that highlights the importance of considering the use of technology as a complementary measuring tool in any such investigation.

In general, such studies relate to the field of marketing, and often serve as a way of confirming the emotional response generated by a given product or advertising campaign. This current investigation represents an attempt to incorporate emotional response data recording, and its interpretation as an integral variable in a project's development from its initial stages, so as to better guide its evolution in terms of variables such as its functionality, ergonomics, and usability.

QUANTIFYING EMOTIONS

Our brain has a series of automatic mechanisms, or subconscious reactions, which can be monitored both via our brain activity and from the point of view of their behavioral and psychophysiological consequences. This additional information allows us to understand the behavior of human beings in a more clear and precise way.

As indicated by Braidot (2005), surveys, in-depth interviews, and focus groups can only provide superficial information about the underlying causes that relate to consumer behavior. This is due to the fact that the answers to both a questionnaire and a guided conversation during motivational research obtain information based exclusively on conscious reflexion, when actually most of our choices originate from unconscious reasoning. The key lays now not so much in the analysis of what clients say, or in monitoring the way they act, but rather in investigating the underlying causes behind their behavior.

Every time the brain is submitted to stimulus via the senses (sight, hearing, touch, etc.), its activity and the related consequences from a psychophysiological and behavioral point of view appear as a series of signals (electrical, magnetic, chemical etc). Different technologies have been developed to measure this activity, such as functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI), magnetoencephalography (MEG), positron emission tomography (PET), and electromyography (EMG). However, the application of these technologies remains complicated and they are not currently viable for use in real-life situations.

As a result, in this research paper we have taken a special interest in those technologies whose evolution and development in recent years have demonstrated a significant improvement in access to these devices, allowing a far wider group of professionals to employ them in their studies.

Galvanic skin response (GSR) or skin conductance response (SCR)

This technology is famous for forming the basis of the well-known polygraph or lie detector. It is based on the fact that our skin's electrical resistance changes in response to our emotional changes.

It measures the conductance of the skin, among other indicators, to infer the level of activation (excitement) of the subject. This activation is fundamental in regulating consciousness, attention span, as well as the processing of information, and is a crucial element in the motivation of specific behavior.

Portable electroencephalography system (EEG)

The electroencephalography system, or portable EEG, gives us information about the brain areas that are excited when it comes to interacting with different stimuli (colors, sounds, smells, forms, and so on), or when undertaking some kind of activity. As it is a portable system, this information is obtained in a real-life context and not under laboratory conditions, thus providing both qualitative and highly reliable data relating to the subject's experience.

Thanks to the EEG, we are able to measure variables such as emotional valence, cognition, attention span, vision, movement, and recognition.

Facial emotion recognition software

This is a software tool that allows the emotions experienced by the users to be determined through the automatic analysis of facial expressions. It facilitates the detection of the six basic and universal emotions: happiness, sadness, fear, anger, disgust, and surprise, as defined by Ekman (1992).

Furthermore, the software tracks the orientation of the user's head, which allows for a better identification of their facial gestures and, by using a complex algorithm, it identifies the muscles that are involved and analyzes their response in order to indicate which emotion the subject is experiencing at any given moment.

Behavioral analysis software

This software allows us to analyze the behavior of users through the observation of their interaction with the environment, and records behavioral data for subsequent review, analysis, and presentation. Furthermore, the system can be integrated with other devices such as those previously mentioned, in order to generate a more rigorous analysis.

Eye tracking system

This tool does not provide information about an emotional response, but rather acts as a compliment to the study.

It allows us to examine the visual pathways followed by the subject of the study, and thus create maps that signal the 'hot spots' of an image, meaning the areas in which vision is focused

over the longest period of time. It can also indicate the trajectories that the eyes follow and thus the order in which elements are examined. The non-invasive character of the system allows the activity to be carried out without conditioning the interactive experience to the surroundings.

A PRACTICAL EXAMPLE OF APPLICATION

The main goal of this investigation is to demonstrate the possibility of developing products according to emotional parameters, making use of the constant evolution of technology and the desire of researchers to employ these new measuring systems. In addition, the ‘democratization’ of these technologies means that research can move away from its traditional areas of study, towards new disciplines such as marketing and design, allowing us to provide some objectivity to a topic as subjective as our emotions. To best develop this approach, we have opted to integrate these technological resources in a conventional design methodology, and as a practical example they have been applied to the development of a music stand.

The music stand has been relegated to a secondary role within the music world, despite being essential to academic training as well as professional practice. The world of music is an artistic discipline that, as such, incorporates emotion as an inherent property. However, the close relationship that develops between the musician and their instrument is never reached between the musician and the accessories needed for the performance of their activity, and especially not their music stand. This product, as has been shown in the case of this study, generally arouses negative emotions amongst its users, the result perhaps of the non-inclusion of certain ergonomics of emotional criteria in its design and development; conceivably as a consequence of its lack of evolution, or because of its complexity of use, both in terms of erecting and dismantling, and in the context of user-product interaction.

The development of this practical example was performed under a conventional design methodology (Figure 1), which covers everything from the strategical product definition and conceptual design to its engineering, production, and so on. Throughout the different developmental phases, we incorporated some of the aforementioned devices.

Senso-perceptive session

In the second stage of the design process, an activity called ‘Senso-perceptive session employing touch’ was held with the objective of identifying those materials and/or surface finishes that are more pleasing to touch, and which evoke a feeling of a higher quality of product. It was carried out using facial emotion recognition software that allowed us to identify emotions during the interaction between users and materials, and to visualize the results instantly.

The session took place in two phases, one being objective-behavioral and the other subjective-cognitive. Both are important, but on this occasion, the goal was to determine the

emotional impact of the different possible materials as potential components of the completed music stand.

During the session, the subjects could not see the materials they were touching with their hands, therefore eliminating ‘contaminating elements’, which we understand as being small cognitive processes that prompt the subjects to interpret the colors and forms of the materials, creating connections and associations that did not form the object of the study.

In this way, the emotional facial expression of each of the subjects was analyzed during their tactile exploration of the materials, allowing us to analyze the instant emotional reaction that arises when the tactile perceptive system comes into contact with materials of different texture.

We would like to highlight the informative power that the perceptive tactile system provides, since the participating subjects of the research use their own hands as their main work tool. This information is fundamental, since musicians have a daily and constant interaction with their music stand. By determining which emotions different materials evoke, we can create emotional ties between the music stand and the musician. It has been proven throughout history that positive emotions create connections and establish associations with the individual that reinforce their current behavior, increasing the probability that this same behavior will be repeated in the future.

Once we had obtained objective and behavioral data, subjects were asked how they felt when touching the material. This question was associated with the so-called emotional valence, hedonistic value or the pleasure-displeasure scale. Subjects were allowed freedom to express their opinions and beliefs about what they considered they had touched, as well as expressing the different associations made between their perception and their past experiences with other objects that they find similar.

Figure 1. Methodology

83.33% of our sample (28 subjects) stated categorically that had they seen the materials, they would have reacted differently, because by seeing the colors and shapes, the emotion they displayed would not have been the same. Therefore, the sensory integration of the stimulus following different methods completes the processing of attributed information to such stimulus, reducing the informative power of those emotions measured in an indirect way.

Video catalog

At the end of the fourth stage, a new test was performed using facial emotion recognition software, combined with a brief questionnaire. The session was carried out on each of the participants individually, and it is important to point out that at no time during the session briefing were subjects informed that the prototype being developed had been included in the video catalog along with other types of music stand. This was done intentionally, since we were interested in finding out if they recognized it, and what the sensations were that it provoked among them. The two graphs included in Figure 2 show subjects' emotions at two different times whilst viewing the video catalog. It can be seen that at the beginning there is no clear dominance of any of the emotions measured by the software, whereas in the second graph, which corresponds to the time interval in which the prototype under development was shown, the prominent emotion is happiness.

Figure 2. Measurement of time-dependent emotion

Musician-music stand interaction

After the prototype had been manufactured, a fifth stage was carried out in which users could experience the product first-hand, see the advantages of the prototype compared to the conventional music stand, and at the same time evaluate all the criteria that had been established when it was created. The session was divided into two parts: in the first part, the user read sheet music from the prototype, and in the second part they repeated the activity using a conventional foldable stand. The 'wind' parameter, simulated by a fan, was maintained constant for both parts, since wind is one of the main issues that musicians encounter when performing outdoors. Both the concentration level and the attention level required for the interaction were evaluated. In order to do so, an eye tracking system was used (Figure 3), which was capable of registering the movements of the human eye and determining the main points of focus, along with a galvanic skin response receptor that allows us to measure the subject's level of excitement. The visual mapping results obtained during the interaction with both stands, showed that with the prototype, users' eyes are directed at the center of the support, helping them to achieve a higher level of concentration, whereas focus is more dispersed when using the conventional stand.

Figure 3. Eye Tracking

The galvanic response data shows three phases, which can be seen in Figure 4. The first is marked by stable and prolonged electrodermal activity, up until the user's direct interaction with the prototype. In the second phase, during the interaction with the stand, we observed a marked rise in EDA (electrodermal activity), mainly obtained due to the user's lack of knowledge about the use of the prototype. Throughout this phase, a small series of regular peaks can be observed, due to this inexperience and lack of knowledge. Lastly, during the third phase a constant level of excitement is established, caused by playing the instrument during interaction with the music stand. This promotes a significant rise in the internal

Figure 4. Galvanic response

control locus of the subject; we attribute this to the positive consequences of the interaction with their skills as musicians and not to other external causes.

As can be observed in the graph, the electrodermal activity measurements obtained from the device on the conventional stand are constant, with only slight variations. From this it can be deduced that despite the great familiarity that the subjects have with the music stand, since it does not have an adequate design, peaks of excitement are produced that translate into increases and decreases of the EDA. In this way, concentration and attention levels can be lowered significantly owing to poor interaction with what is essentially an unintuitive design.

CONCLUSIONS

In order to help facilitate the dissemination and implementation of emotional design and to promote research and development, in this paper we have shown a practical example based on a methodology of conventional design, but which relies on the use of certain tools, measurement techniques, and behavioral and psychophysiological measurements stemming from the study of emotions. During the course of the research certain limitations have emerged, but the results gained have been satisfactory and allow the validation, to a greater or lesser extent, of the study's initial main goals. The validation process allows us to demonstrate that the prototype developed was perceived in a very positive manner by the users, indicating that the developments made were adapted, to a large extent, to the functional and emotional expectations detected in the initial phases of the project.

The main contributions of this research can be summarized as follows: firstly, the demonstration, in both theoretical and practical areas, that it is possible to develop products with emotional criteria together with a set of techniques and tools of conventional design methodologies, without resorting to more specific, complicated, and difficult-to-implement methodologies. Secondly, affirmation that a product provokes emotion, and that this should be an inherent quality of any product, not only a marketing strategy. This research supports the idea that this claim can only be sustained through continuous monitoring of the emotional needs of users in different

phases of the design process. Thirdly, we can achieve a more reliable measurement of the emotional state of the user during their interaction with a product by measuring physiological, cognitive, and behavioral dimensions.

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SAY, WHAT DID YOU SEE? A QUALITATIVE INTERVIEW REVEALS HOW USERS INTERPRETED GUI ICONS

Martha Skogen
Norwegian University of Science & Technology (NTNU)
Trondheim, Norway
✉ martha.skogen@ntnu.no

ABSTRACT

A comprehensive user test was conducted with 29 participants, 11 of whom were aged five to twelve. The intention of the exploratory computer-based test was to collect both quantitative and qualitative information—this article reviews the qualitative data only. After the user test, each participant answered identical, open-ended questions regarding his/her approach(es) to the task. Data was split into <13 (Youths) and >17 (Adults). The age groups' responses are compared: Youths' responses were often succinct, direct, and confident compared with the long, detailed, and verbose responses from the Adults. Adults often contradicted themselves whereas Youths did not. In order to categorize the participants' diverse experiences, responses were analyzed for target words. The potential for design biases is highlighted. It is recommended that designers verbally test their specific user group—often—during the HCI/GUI design process in order to avoid designing from their own perspective and misunderstanding their user group entirely.

KEYWORDS: *Human-computer interaction, GUI design, user test, computer icons, visual design bias*

INTRODUCTION

This exploratory research focuses on how people interpret computerized visual stimulation. In this case, on-screen icons are the subject of investigation. The approach involves asking participants to view a fixed set of icons and collecting their responses, and determining if any patterns arise from the data. Of particular interest is if users respond that certain aspects of visual design are more influential than others (e.g. contrast, color, photorealism, perspective, number of metaphors, adherence to archetype, etc.). It seems logical that the more elements we are presented with onscreen, the more we are required to visually 'digest' those elements; and vast data in the field of attention has confirmed this. Two research groups say it well: 'Our environment contains much more sensory information than we can process at any given time' (Liu & Mance, 2011, p26), and 'people can respond to only a small amount of the sensory information present at any moment' (Corbetta et al., 1990, p. 1556). Visual processing takes valuable time and energy, especially when the extra visual elements are redundant and unnecessary. In this era where computers are becoming increasingly entwined in our everyday lives, our visual sense is immersed in ever-increasing amounts of stimuli. There surely must be a saturation point

somewhere. Due to these factors, it becomes even more important for HCI/GUI designers to use streamlined visual interfaces to reduce cognitive load, reduce the potential for stress and increase a user's effectiveness when s/he interacts with a computerized device. In short, this researcher ascertains that visual information should be as simple and effective as possible in all human-computer interface tools.

Several studies support the use of simple visual design over complicated visual design: Chiu et al. (2012); Davis & Swezey (1983); Huang et al. (2002); Gittins (1986); McDougall et al. (2000); McDougall & Reppa (2008); Reppa et al. (2008); Yan (2011) etc. Byrne sums it up:

for icons to be effective aids to visual search, they must be simple and easily discriminable ...

They (icons) seem to clutter the display with information that participants are unable to employ to their advantage (Byrne, 1993).

There is a large amount of research regarding how icons affect the participant's experience and how to design icons effectively. However, these studies do not distinguish between all age groups. Studies with adults and seniors are prevalent, whereas studies comparing adults with children are virtually absent. This is not a good idea as children/youth's

computer experience is continuously on the rise (Rocheleau, 1995). Children and youths represent an important participant group (Chiasson, & Gutwin, 2005), and it is important that their needs be taken into account (Druin, 1999). Not all user groups are included regularly, despite such acknowledgments from researchers (e.g. Adams et al):

Within HCI, there is also the recognition that the focus on tasks is not enough to design and implement an effective system. There is also a growing need to understand how user issues are subjectively and collectively experienced and perceived by different user groups (Adams et al., 2008, p. 138)

This article describes one data set of a computer-based user test that incorporated both quantitative (via participant ranking) and qualitative (via post-test interview) techniques. According to Adams et al. (2008), this multiple approach (i.e. gathering numerous sets of data simultaneously) embodies the true intention of grounded theory research. The user test was conducted in a modern computer laboratory setting (Jensen & Skov, 2005) where conventional computer-interface icons were used as an example of low-level visual stimuli. ‘Low-level’ in this context refers to the icons’ relatively small size and apparently limited amount of two-dimensional visual information. This researcher considers computer-based icons as anything but visually limited—they are miniature, independent visual compositions. The research behind this article investigates the independent (albeit small) nature of computer icons’ visual composition, not their meta-level position within applications or on the screen itself.

GUI designers face numerous challenges while designing apparently humble little compositions such as the computer icon. The question at the root of the design process is: What are the primary visual factors that GUI designers must control? A large body of literature attests to the importance of considering numerous aspects (‘parameters’) of the icon’s visual design. Näsänen & Ojanpää (2003) found that contrast affects the speed of icon interpretation—the speed by which icons can be searched for—was clearly dependent on image contrast at small values, but relatively independent at high contrast values. Lindberg & Näsänen (2003) found that although icon spacing does not have an effect on search times, the size of the interface elements has a great effect. Huang (2007) showed that four visual variables significantly affected search performance: figure/background color combinations, type of computer icon, figure/background area ratio. Skogen (forthcoming) found that there are age differences in how simple and complicated icons are interpreted. In fact, interpretation of an icon appeared to be completely contradictory in many cases. Although there is abundant research regarding icons’ visual parameters and how to design them, there is a lack of research on how these visual design parameters are interpreted by children/youths. Indeed, numerous HCI design studies use adults as test participants—as stated above, adults do not represent the full spectrum of computer users.

From a study from Skogen (forthcoming), Youths <thirteen years old seemed to recognize the detail-rich and highly realistic icons faster than the abstracted, rectilinear ones,

based upon their ranking of those icons first (equivalent to the “pickup order” described in Skogen, 2006). Adults responded initially to the icons that showed fewer details. Although there were no participants to demonstrate it, there appeared to be a shift between ages thirteen and seventeen, after which users began to respond similarly to the Adults. From this, we can deduct that the descriptors associated with the terms ‘simple’ and ‘complicated’ do not apply to all participant groups.

For this user test, participants of varying age groups did not interpret GUI icons in the same manner.

At the end of the user test, participants took a short post-test verbal interview intended to give them an opportunity to discuss, explain and/or clarify the criteria they thought about and the strategies they employed during the test. The fundamental point of the short, open-ended qualitative interview revolved around how participants interpret the visual icons. The study was exploratory, lacked a formal hypothesis, and gathered quantitative and qualitative data simultaneously. The fundamental purpose for the post-test qualitative interview was to gather verbatim information regarding:

- What particular words did participants use to a.) Describe their approach(es); b.) Describe the criteria they thought about; and/or c.) Describe the strategies that they used to rank the icons?

This final research topic forms the basis of this article.

METHOD

This exploratory user test was conducted at the National Center for Patient Journal Research computer lab at St. Olav’s hospital, Trondheim, Norway. The equipment was conventional: a modern Microsoft PC with mouse and flat screen sat at a standard table with a comfortable chair. The room was airy, uncluttered, quiet and well lit (with windows to a natural setting outside). The test environment was intentionally set up to represent a basic computer room that a participant might have at home. Participants were given an identical set of instructions on a sheet of paper (to ensure consistency), which asked them to view sets of icons on a computer screen. If the participant was too young to read, then a parent read it for them.

The computer test included a set of icons (ten sets in total), where each set of icons represented one theme: e.g. *Home*, *PC*, and *Trash*. The icon sets were (in order): *Search*, *Edit*, *Document*, *Mouse*, *Mail*, *Home*, *Print*, *Book*, *Trash*, *PC*. This set (including its specific sequencing) was intended to duplicate the format of the pilot study (Skogen, 2006), with one major change: this user test would be conducted in the computer icons’ native media, the computer. However, unlike the pilot study, this user test included two extra categories (*Search* and *Edit*) at the beginning. This gave the participant time to become familiar with the test format, so that when they encountered the original eight categories (i.e. *Document* – *PC*),

participants were seated comfortably, accustomed to computer/mouse's functionality, and familiar with the user test's format and progression. Each participant completed the user test individually, while the researcher was present at all times, seated discreetly to the side and behind. This provided the participant with a sense of security—the researcher was available for questions (particularly with the younger participants) and silently took notes. Although the researcher's presence may have influenced the users' responses, this is impossible to know. They said afterwards that they were undisturbed by her presence, and most participants stated that they'd forgotten she was there.

For each icon set, the participant saw eight icons of one theme appear on the screen at one time (see Fig. 1 below). The test consisted of ten sets/themes of icons, eight icons per set. The set of icons appeared in a circular format as shown below (Fig. 1). When the user was finished with one theme, s/he pressed *Next* to bring up the next theme. Time was not recorded and there was no time limit. To avoid potential bias due to an icon's placement in the circle, the computer repositioned the icons randomly with every reload. This means that each participant saw the icons in a randomized, unique relationship to each other, yet always in the same circular format. The other elements on the screen (instructional text, scale, button placement) remained constant for all participants. The participant was instructed to drag-and-drop each icon to one box on the scale. Each box could contain only one icon.

After completing the ranking for a set, the participant moved to the next icon theme by clicking 'Next', whereupon the next circular set of icons appeared immediately. Participants were encouraged to respond quickly, not to think too much, and to trust their first reaction. Three types of data were collected for each participant:

1. Ranking of the icons (for quantitative data collection)
2. Video recording of the test in progress, with permission (for later reference/review)
3. Post-test interview responses for categorization purposes (for qualitative data collection)

The video apparatus was mounted very clearly on the top of the computer screen. Each participant granted permission to record prior to the test. The researcher's role was to be available as a 'guide' during the test, unobtrusive yet available. She served to help with computer formalities only, and avoided influencing any answers of the test itself. Only a few of the participants needed her assistance at all.

Quantitative Data—Participants Rank the Icons

As stated earlier, the quantitative results (Skogen, forthcoming) revealed an unforeseen age difference: detail-rich icons termed *Complicated* were often ranked lower on the scale (i.e. closer to *Simple*) for the Youths. The Adults responded in a predictable way, however the Youths did not. The results imply that designers unwittingly carry inherent biases regarding how icons and their visual parameters appear to various users across all age groups. It appears that one design does not fit all, and designers should not presume that they do. This will be discussed in the section, 'Discussion' below.

Qualitative Data—Post-Test Interview

The researcher spoke the native language of the participant (English or Norwegian), and each participant responded in his/her native language. The intention of the post-test interview was to gather participants' descriptive words regarding (in order of importance):

Figure 1. "PC" themed-icons: a screenshot from the user test

- a. The criteria and strategies each participant used to rank the icons
- b. How each participant defined the words “Simple” and “Complicated”
- c. Closing the test in an appropriate & natural manner (rather than the participant leaving the room immediately).

The five Open-Ended Interview Questions were (in order):

1. Did you enjoy the test?
2. Can you describe the criteria and/or strategies you used to place the icons—what did you think about?
Rephrased for the Youths: How did you choose where each icon should go—what did you think about?
3. How did you define *Simple* and *Complicated*?
4. Did you find anything particularly easy or difficult?
5. When asked to think of one single icon from the test, which one comes to mind?

At the end of the test, the participants often pushed their chair back and paused... some of them had used only four minutes to take the entire test so they were slightly out of breath. The difference between Youths’ and Adults’ responses began to appear at this moment of test completion: almost all of the Adults started talking immediately upon finishing the test, whereas all the Youths looked quietly back towards the researcher and waited for instructions on what to do next. Regarding the answers themselves, very often the Adults’ responses were obtuse and self-contradictory. For the Adults, the researcher frequently needed to prompt the participant to be more specific in his/her response, give examples, or try to describe more clearly what they were thinking. Regarding question two, the Adults often answered in a confusing or wordy manner, almost as if they were trying to impress the researcher. Youths responded very directly and concisely. This also will be addressed in detail in the section ‘Discussion’ below.

ANALYSIS

Limits of Language

It is important to recognize that everything—including open-ended responses—is open to interpretation.

By the very act of using language, a person already filters the type of information that their mind’s eye can see.

This phenomenon can be described with an example from an eight year old’s responses to the interview questions. When asked which icon he recalled from the test, he said ‘the computer’. When asked ‘Which one?’, he answered, ‘The one that looks like a simple one!’ In his mind’s eye, he knew exactly which one he was talking about, but the nature of linguistics prevented this researcher from understanding which one he meant. Language is a crude tool for seeing into another person’s inner thoughts. This is contrary to Munslow’s postulate that:

History owes its very nature to the fact that language is an incredibly rich medium for describing and explaining the meaning of objects in the world. (Narrative and History - Theory and History. James, 2007, p.34).

Categories

For analysis of the five Open-Ended Questions, we used grounded-theory techniques described by Bryant et al. (2007); Charmaz (2006); Clarke & Friese (2007); and Seale et al., (ed.) (2004). Kvale & Brinkman (2009) provided numerous helpful tips on interviewing techniques in general. Ryghaug (2002) offers a nice outline of various methods of text analysis, including structuralism, semiotics, and ‘linguistic-based analysis methods’, but she does not go into specific detail regarding exactly how to do it.

As per the quantitative data set (Skogen, forthcoming), verbal responses were first split into two age groups: <17 (Youths) and >17 (Adults). This was done to maintain consistency across both sets of data.

For the qualitative/interview data set, analysis began with dividing all responses into two major groups, ‘*Criteria*’ and ‘*Strategy*’. *Criteria* was regarded as noun-based and referred to ‘what’ the user did, whereas *Strategy* was more verb-based and referred to ‘how’ the user did it. After this division, words were allowed to rise out of the two groups. Although seemingly diverse, participants’ responses showed that common words were often used (regardless of native language). All responses were analyzed, and sorted according to those word commonalities. These commonalities quickly revealed ‘target words’: i.e. words that arose more often than other descriptors. Upon scoring of the target words, the titles of the categories became evident. The specificity of the target words grew outward to encompass the words that participants (collectively) had used to describe a particular visual parameter of the icons. These target words were then codified into larger categories.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Emotional Value of Responses

After documentation of every word of the post-test interview, the emotional value of the responses became noticeable, based upon age. The Youths displayed an unassuming self-confidence, chose direct words, and answered the questions bluntly, sometimes monosyllabically. Adults often (but not always) responded in a verbose, complicated manner, and their answers were sometimes self-contradicting or did not make sense at all. The Youths answered the question, without pause or second thought, and then waited for the next—they responded to the open-ended questions very clearly. Not once during the Youth’s interviews did the researcher sense an awkward pause, yet this was almost common with the Adults.

During the interview, it was important to avoid offering deeper clarification of the five Interview Questions due to:

1. Need to maintain consistency
2. Not wanting to impose vocabulary upon the participant
3. Avoidance of leading questions.

On a few occasions the researcher was compelled to expand upon the questions, but this only occurred in the rare instances where the extended pause felt too awkward for both the participant and the researcher. In these cases, she repeated the question, with slight rewording and/or encouragement to continue. For the few instances where it did happen, it occurred only with Adults. With the Youths, there was no need to clarify.

There were no pauses where the Youths seemed to fail to understand the question, nor did the Youths hesitate or take time to prepare an answer. This shows yet another level of age differences between *Simple* (i.e. Youths') and *Complicated* (i.e. Adults') responses. The researcher was often caught off guard by the Youths' verbal responses because there was no way to be prepared for the succinctness and clarity of their answers. Due to the Youths' concise, clear, direct answers, the interviews with the Youths went very quickly. Although she realized the Youths responded effectively at the time, it was not possible to fully experience the Youths' confident directness until she analyzed their videoed responses.

Contrarily, some of the Adults' descriptions of their criteria, strategies, and other answers seemed to flow into each other, and for some participants, answers became almost interchangeable. Even upon review of the videos, some of the Adults' sentences were convoluted to the point that it was difficult to discern what they were trying to say. Indeed, categorizing the use of language proved to be more difficult than anticipated. Still, the words were tallied and specific usage was documented. The words were important, and the general communicability of the participants' answers did not affect the categorization. However, it served as an interesting observation (between Youths and Adults) only.

Categories

i. Color

The target word '*color/farge*' came up often, and there didn't seem to be another word that participants used to communicate that particular aspect of the icons' design. One 9-year-old pinpointed *color* (while simultaneously using the word *simple/enkel* on two occasions):

...det var noe med enkelte som jeg likte veldig godt. Jeg likte dem med farger.

Farger var litt enkelere.

(*There was something about the simple ones that I liked very much. I liked those with color. Color was a little more simple.*)

COLOR became one of the codified categories because the participants used it often. However, as the quantitative/rank-

ing data from this user test revealed, there may be an inherent bias lurking in the use of the word 'color'. Some participants had very different interpretations of color: a few participants decided icons were *Simple because* they contained color, whereas other participants decided that icons were *Complicated* because they contained color. Those who said color made an icon *Complicated*, also said that black & white icons were more *Simple* than the colored ones. Regardless, it was only the Youths who considered color to be a simplifying parameter (perhaps making the icon appear more realistic). Contrarily, the Adults considered color to be a more complicating parameter. This disparity in interpretation of this one parameter—COLOR—between Youths and Adults is perhaps one of the most important results of this study.

ii. Recognizability

Many participants described another parameter of the icons' visual impression: its ability to communicate meaning quickly—it's recognizability. This refers to an icons' ability to represent what it was supposed to represent, i.e. whether it was easy/difficult to understand what the icon described. The terms used for this became coded as RECOGNIZABILITY.

iii. Detail

Many participants described the icons' richness of detail, which quickly became coded as DETAIL.

Again, target words were easy to identify due to '*detail*' being used in a consistent manner. Only one person mentioned '*perspective*', while another person mentioned '*photorealism*' only once.

iv. Degree of Abstraction

Many participants found it difficult to describe the concept of visual simplicity without using the word 'simple'.

From this user test (particularly the quantitative data herein) we may deduce that each participant carries an individualized idea of what 'simple design' means, and this term's interpretive emotional value might be linked to the user's age. Simplicity appears to be in the eyes of the beholder. Indeed, a 'simple' icon means something different when viewed from an Adult's viewpoint when compared with a Youth's or a child's viewpoint. This researcher states: the presumption that 'simple' means lack of detail is inherently biased and implies that an adult's viewpoint is the only one that exists. McDougall showed that an icon's concreteness (i.e. the extent to which icons pictorially represent objects, places, or people) primarily affects the grasp of meaning (McDougall et al., 2000), as well as correlates strongly with the ease of an icon's interpretation (McDougall et al., 2006). For this study, the concept of concreteness became expanded and termed as DEGREE of ABSTRACTION.

All of the categories can very easily meld into each other, yet Adult participants seemed to switch quickly between two specific categories, DETAIL and DEGREE of ABSTRACTION.

This quick switching could even occur mid-sentence. One adult participant stated: ‘Line drawings are easier than photorealistic ones and less items makes it easier, makes it simpler’. This participant felt he needed to elaborate on his first sentence (DETAIL) by supporting it with another (DEGREE of ABSTRACTION). Although DETAIL and DEGREE of ABSTRACTION can easily overlap, this researcher intends to keep them separate as much as possible.

Other Creative Descriptors

Some descriptions did not fit into any categorical sorting, yet they became interesting because of their insightfulness and uniqueness. One unforgettable example came from the youngest participant (five years old):

I think the simpler things are harder to break.

The most simple things are the most hard to break, they are!

This was such a profoundly new and unpredicted approach to the task, that it took a few moments to actually comprehend it. Imagine a category entitled Breakability! This participant was a big, strong five-year-old, who (his mother mentioned later) was prone to breaking his toys, so this made perfect sense to him—this ideology of breakability fit into his world seamlessly. He was accustomed to it.

Historicity. A second example is the thirteen-year-old who used a unique technique—historical reference—to determine his definition of *Simple/Complicated*. He was the only one who did so:

Enkle var de som var historiske... kompliserte var moderne.

(*Simple were those that were historical, Complicated were modern.*)

Replicability. When one eleven-year-old was asked what he thought about during the test, he responded:

Det jeg tenkte på var hvis du skal lage... tegne de tingene der... hvor lang tid skal du ta?

(*What I thought about was if you were to make...draw those things there...how long would it take?*)

This participant’s strategy had been to convert each icon into an estimation of his time required to replicate it by drawing it. This idea was actually conveyed by two of the youths, completely independent of each other. This participant was eleven years old and the other individual who used this approach was seventeen years old. Unfortunately this study did not include enough participants to determine how likely would it be for an adult to employ a similar strategy. A criteria/strategy could become its own category if there were enough respondents to support it.

Finally, three of the Adults (all female) strategically interpreted how the icons would appear to others. This was unique among the Adults... none of the Youths used this tactic.

The final four categories were:

1. COLOR
2. RECOGNIZABILITY

3. DETAIL

4. DEGREE of ABSTRACTION

Icon Recall

The fifth Interview Question asked for the participant to recall one specific icon from the test. The intention here was to see which icon made enough of an impression to remain memorable beyond the conclusion of the test. Interestingly, there was only one icon that was recalled by more than one participant (five in total: four Adults and one Youth). It was a highly unusual, detailed and colorful rendering of a house (‘home’). It was also the icon deemed most ‘*Complicated*’ by all Adults. Table one below shows the icon with its corresponding ranking scores for both Adults and Youths (on a scale of 1=*Simple* to 8=*Complicated*).

	ADULTS (>16)	YOUTHS (<13)	ALL AGES COMBINED
 Home	7.6	4.8	6.4

Table 1. The most-recalled icon with ranking scores

All other participants recalled only one instance of other icons.

CONCLUSION

In describing the criteria used to rank the icons, participants in this user test revealed numerous strategies regarding what they thought about while ranking the icons on a scale of *Simple-Complicated*. Some participants used unique and highly insightful approaches whereas the majority showed commonalities among their responses. The fact that we could identify, group, and extract four categories from those target words shows that there were similar approaches to interpreting the icons. Although people used the same target words, (e.g. COLOR), this does *not* infer they interpreted or defined that word similarly.

This is the most important point of the qualitative aspect of this user test, perhaps the largest contribution: designers cannot presume that users will see their designs in the exact same manner. This study showed that there appeared to be age and individual differences in how people interpreted the visual parameter of COLOR. As this one example shows, the viewer’s definitions might be contradictory. If this is the case, how many other visual parameters do we misjudge? It is important for those involved with computer interface design to know the potential for this discrepancy among their users.

This user test incorporated a small sample size (n=29) and although all ages were not represented, it does accomplish a very important task for GUI/HCI designers: it highlights the potential for inherent biases. As adults, we tend to design

from our own perspective, and this means that our designs potentially carry a quiet, unintentional bias. We presume that our definitions of the numerous aspects of visual design apply equally to all age groups (children, adults, and seniors, across cultural boundaries), while this study shows that such presumptions may be highly incorrect.

Designing from one's own adult perspective is a trap into which many GUI designers fall. The only way to avoid this trap is to test the user group repeatedly to ensure that it is the user group's interpretation of the design that is being met, not the designer's. In order to avoid this pitfall, a GUI designer must test often, particularly during the beginning phases of the design process. The most effective time to test is as early as possible, when design changes are easily made. Otherwise, a designer has the potential to miss his/her target user group entirely. Repeated user testing, during *all* phases of the design process, is the only insurance that the designer has—it's the only way s/he can be sure to meet the needs of the intended user group. According to Thomson (2008, p.1):

Indeed, the perspectives of children and young people are of interest to contemporary social scientists precisely because they offer specific and unique insights...which can easily slip below the horizons of older inquirers. The omission of these perspectives can easily lead to researchers making interpretations and representations that are very shortsighted and which miss the point.

This study shows that youths' do not share the same visual design needs for GUI/HCI applications as adults. In addition, people's interpretation of visual information changes as we age. It appears that a GUI icon's visual design—its simplicity and/or visual complexity—is in the eye of the beholder.

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EXPERIENCES AND SENSES AN EXPERIMENTAL BASED METHODOLOGY FOR THE DESIGN OPTIMIZATION

Elia Gatti, Monica Bordegoni, Serena Camere
Dipartimento di Meccanica, Politecnico di Milano
✉ elia.gatti@polimi.it, monica.bordegoni@polimi.it, serena.camere@polimi.it

ABSTRACT

Understanding users' points of view is rapidly becoming an urgent issue for companies and designers, as well as User Experience and Experience Design proving to be of wide interest for academic research. This paper presents an experimental-based methodology aimed at guiding designers during product optimisation. It is meant to support designers in choosing the right strategy to assess the users' emotional reaction towards a product at an early stage of product development. The methodology consists of three different phases: 1) Design Challenge definition, to help in clarifying the research question; 2) Interaction Study, aimed at understanding the user experience; 3) Sensory Boost phase, to improve the products perceived pleasurableness. The methodology includes a review of the methods and tools used for catching users' emotional reactions to products. Moreover, a computer-based version of the methodology will be introduced, together with two case studies to validate the developed methodology.

KEYWORDS: *Emotional Design, User Experience, Methodology, Sensory Boost.*

INTRODUCTION

In today's market world, differentiating products from competitors' is a fundamental matter for industries that want to stand up and gain the preference of consumers (Spence and Gallace 2011). In order to differentiate their offers, producers reached closer to the consumer preferences, by developing products studied not only to provide better usability and interaction, but also to elicit positive emotional reactions in the consumer (Khalid and Helander, 2006). In the design and consumer research, importance of both pragmatic and hedonic-emotional aspects of the products has been theorized and supported by several authors, particularly fitting into the concept of experience design (Shedroff, 2001). The present paper introduces a methodology to support designers in the optimization of the product from an experience design perspective. It consists in a collection of experimental methods aiming at gathering information from the user, thus providing the designer with the data necessary to augment his/her understanding of the consumer's experience.

The methodology in the User Experience Design framework

Since Donald Norman's seminal works (Norman, 2002), the importance of users' emotions and personal needs in the design process has been considered as a crucial point in product design. This view has evolved nowadays into the core principles of User Experience Design (UXD). UXD plays on the emotional and personal needs of the users, placing as much attention as it does on the usability and practical matters, trying to account for the entire experience by involving the users (Shedroff, 2001). According to Forlizzi and Battarbee (2004), designers can consider the experience from a number of perspectives, which have been grouped by the authors into three main categories: *product-centered*, *user-centered*, and *interaction-centered*.

The proposed methodology adopts a conception of experience design from a user-centered perspective (Hassenzahl, 2003, 2008). According to this view, users perceive products according to two main dimensions: pragmatic and hedonic. Pragmatic qualities of a product refer to its ability in accomplishing 'do-goals', which are the purposes for which the object has been created for (for example, a do-goal for a pen is 'write'). Hedonic qualities refer instead to the product's per-

ceived ability to support the achievement of ‘be-goals’. Be-goals represent the hedonic and symbolic needs of the user (referring to the example of the pen, a be-goal for an elegant-shaped pen could be to ‘be professional’, or ‘be elegant’).

In this view, then, the interaction with the product is achieved through the product’s pragmatic and hedonic qualities. Users, in fact, perceive those qualities through their senses. The interaction itself is a motor act allowed by the perception of the features composing the design of the object. In a psychological view, the hedonic features of the object are perceived by senses, and interpreted as being able to satisfy the needs of the user. In the same way, the pragmatic features of the object, that allow the user to use the product for its material purpose, are connected to the user sensory perception. To be usable, a product must match all the sensorial needs of the user, providing all the sensory feedback in the fashion necessary to optimize the accomplishment of the task it has been created for. As an example, it would be pointless creating an alarm not perceivable by the user; the sound of the alarm is needed to recall the user’s attention and to trigger an action.

According to this, our methodology constitutes a procedure, based on experimental methods, which can support designers aiming at augmenting the efficacy of the sensorial feedback underpinning the hedonic and pragmatic features of the product. Indeed, the final goal is to provide the designer with information concerning how the product is perceived and how the sensory characteristics of the product are elaborated by the user brain. This will facilitate the product optimization, thus obtaining a more usable and, eventually, more emotional design.

Experimental based approaches for product design optimization

Over the years, a series of studies have been conducted in the design and marketing fields in order to highlight how to guide the designers in understanding the users’ perception of the product, and therefore spotting the user preferences and implementing them in the design solution. For example, Raz et al. (2008) set up a protocol aiming to act on the sensorial characteristic of the product, based on experimental data collected from consumers. Similar methodologies have been proposed for years in the realm of design of food products and aliments. Ellekjaer et al. (1996) studied a strategy aimed to improve the sensory qualities of a food product, based on

a sensory description of the product followed by multivariate statistical analysis, and a different strategy used to link the user perception of the product with the design solution was reported by Buchenau and Suri (2000). The method, rooted in the co-design realm, involved an active collaboration between users and designers at the prototyping phase.

In 2009 Kaczorowska made the effort of listing a series of methods used nowadays to relate the consumer perception to the product development (Kaczorowska, 2011). He organized the methods according to their appearance in five different phases of the design process: idea generation, concept generation, prototype development, verifying test, and product introduction to marketing. In addition, in order to verify the final solution, Kaczorowska suggested the use of boredom test, preference test, and finally purchase intent test. In the fifth phase, which is the introduction of the product in the market, no method is described.

However, despite the attention that these methods have on the user perception and to his (her) reactions to the product, they do not explicitly fit into the experience design realm. More specifically, in all the cases, when a method investigates the hedonic dimension of a product, it usually ignores the pragmatic one, and vice versa. In this paper we introduce a methodology, which aims to help designers in optimizing their products, providing tools to explore the users’ perception of the product under both the pragmatic and hedonic point of view.

THE METHODOLOGY: A THREE-PHASE PROCESS FOR THE PRODUCT DESIGN OPTIMIZATION

The methodology proposed is composed by three different phases: The Design Question phase, the Interaction Study, and finally the *Sensory Boost* (Figure 1).

In particular, during the first phase the designer highlights and makes clear the design question expressed by the client (marketing experts, customers, etc.). In the second stage, the interaction between user and product is assessed, in order to find the important characteristics of the product that are related to the design question. Finally, a sensory optimization experiment is performed in order to optimize the product by means of cross modal correspondences or threshold measurements.

Figure 1: the methodology

Figure 2: a screenshot of the computer-based version

According to the methodology presented in this paper, a computer-based framework has been developed. In particular, designers interacting with the computer-based framework are presented with information on each stage of the methodology. This information is aimed to help the designer in focusing on the right design question (phase one), in choosing the right method for the user-product interaction (phase two), and in performing the sensory boost (phase three). It is important to note, however, that the designer will be left free to perform all the design choices within each phase, and no preferential way to go through the different steps of the methodology will be provided. (Figure two).

Definition of the design question

The first phase of the methodology can be considered as a preliminary phase, and it is related to the design question to which the designer wishes to answer. Does the client want a more efficacious product? A more usable one? Does the client want to communicate feelings with the object he (she) is going to re-create?

Although it may seem easy, there are many issues that should draw the attention of the designer in clarifying the design question posed by the client. A better understanding of the challenge may reduce the risks of choosing the wrong strategy of experiments, thus allowing for the setting up of the user tests in a more accurate way. In this manner, the designer will be able to focus only on what the customer effectively needs to understand in order to improve the product experience. However, it is not always easy to understand what the client

wants, and often the client cannot be aware of the direction the design process has to take.

As a matter of fact, a first step is to understand, referring to the experience design framework, whether the changes of the product belong to its pragmatic or hedonic characteristics (or even both). Concerning the hedonic characteristic of the product, a guide to better structure the design question can be found in the needs the user wants to satisfy. Sheldon and colleagues (Sheldon et al., 2001) compared ten candidates' psychological needs in an attempt to determine which were truly fundamental for users. They found that autonomy, competence, and relatedness, were consistently among the top four needs, in terms of both their salience and their association with event-related affect. Self-esteem was also important, whereas self-actualization or meaning, physical thriving, popularity or influence, and money-luxury were less important, but still present. It is advisable then, in the optimization, to look at how a given product is able to satisfy these needs, in order to re-define the design question.

At the same time, it could be crucial in the pragmatic optimization to understand whether the user would actually benefit by an augment of the product's performance, either augmenting the user perception of the performance of the product, or keeping the performance of the product constant while diminishing the costs. As a matter of fact, in some cases the designer cannot improve the performance of the product because this would exceed his or her competences. In other cases though, a design aid is useful and even necessary. In these cases a pragmatic optimization would be of great use.

Figure 3 the panel in the computer-based version of the methodology, where the designer is allowed to look through the most appropriate methods by applying some selection filters

Interaction Studies

Once the design question is defined, the second phase of the methodology deals with gathering information on the interaction between user and product by means of the application of experimental methods. The final aim of this stage is to point out which product features are considered important by the user in addressing the design question, so as to subsequently (during the third phase) boost these features. It is important to note that the methodology is not restrictive on which methods to use to relate user and product, as far as this relationship is investigated. The computer-based version of the product currently includes a list of eighteen methods (Figure three), each of them described and explained by means of examples and scientific references.

Moreover, in the computer-based version, a number of filters are available to help the designer in selecting the best experimental methods according to his/her needs and skills. In particular, the filters are: the affordable number of participants, the level of complexity of the experiment (which includes equipment, phases, set up, prototypes, etc.), the supposed skills in analysing data (some of the tools may require high statistical skills), the contribution the experiment brings in addressing a pragmatic question, the contribution the experiment brings in addressing a hedonic question, and a further categorisation of the methods and tools, explicit or implicit. In fact, explicit experiments include an explicit assessment of the participants on the tested object, while implicit experiments do not necessarily ask the participant for feedback on the interaction itself.

The explicit experiments so far included in the computer-based version of the methodology are:

- Questionnaires (i.e., Gentile, Spiller, Noci, 2007).
- Written analysis (i.e., Fenko, Schifferstein, and Hekkert, 2010).
- Cards sorting (i.e., Chen and Occena, 1999).
- Attrakdiff (i.e., Hassenzhal, Burmester, Koller, 2003).
- Sensory snapshot (i.e., Moskovitz, 2004).
- Quality function deployment (i.e., Costa, Dekker, and Jongen, 2000).
- Product Emotion Measurement instrument (PrEmo) (i.e., Desmet, Hekkert, and Jacobs, 2000).
- Self-Assessment Manikin (SAM) (Bradley and Lang, 1985).
- Emotion wheel (Sacharin, Schlegel, and Scherer 2012).

Among them, a specific role is covered by the methods applying multivariate statistics to the data, such as Multi-Dimensional Scaling, and the final stages of Conjoint Analysis and Semantic Differentials Method. These methods deserve a separate classification because, despite the fact they ask direct assessment about the product, they also provide further implicit information about how consumers interpret and categorize the products. The methods based on multivariate analysis included in the computer-based methodology are:

- Conjoint Analysis. (i.e., Moskovitz et al., 2005).
- Multi-Dimensional Scaling (MDS) for the perceptual space (i.e., Giboreau et al., 2001).

- Semantic Differentials Method (SDM) (i.e., Osgood et al., 1957).
- Kansei engineering (Nagamachi, 2008).

Instead, the implicit experiments so far treated by the methodology are:

- Eye tracking. (i.e., Piqueras-Fiszman et al., 2012).
- Body tracking. (i.e., Bianchi-Berthouze et al., 2006)
- Implicit Association Test (IAT). (i.e., Parise and Spence, 2012).
- Evaluation of the physiological activation. (i.e., Picard, 2003).
- Neural activations (i.e., Picard, 2003).

The second phase of the methodology offers a comprehensive review of tools, but it is still far from being exhaustive of all the experimental methods adopted during the years to study products' perception. It is, in fact, a starting point. Further methods will be implemented in the future.

Sensory Boost

The last phase actually represents the core of the methodology. In fact, most of the works on design optimization stop after achieving information from the methods listed in the interaction phase. It is theoretically possible to improve a product without going through the sensory boost phase. For example, obtaining an optimized product would be possible after conjoint analysis or QFD. Unfortunately, however, these improvements often lead to trade-offs between the features to improve (and/or to add), the price of the product (which usually rises), and other features that might be related with the original setting of the product (Green & Srinivasan, 1978; Zarei et al., 2011).

Let us imagine, for example, that the users' preference for a cell-phone or a tablet is driven by the luminosity of the screen. The brighter the screen, the more the users like the product. Let us then suppose that for each Watt of luminosity the battery of the tablet lasts for a little less time, which is obviously not convenient nor appreciated by the user. In this case, a trade off analysis is usually performed, in order to maximize the benefit of adding luminosity and minimize the drawback of losing battery autonomy. However, it seems legitimate to ask: Is this trade-off that necessary? In the field of sensory science, it is well known that there is a relationship between background and perceived brightness (e.g. Cohen & Grossberg, 1984). It would therefore likely be possible, then, that instead of performing a trade-off on the tablet, the color or the size of the frame of the screen could be changed, so as to augment its perceived brightness without influencing the battery's performance and endurance.

The aim of the sensory boost is, indeed, to assess these kinds of optimization, retrieving information concerning users' sensory perception of the important product features, trying to enhance them in a perceptive way. According to the methodology outlined here, two main ways of investigating users'

perception are the study of crossmodal correspondences and the use of psychophysical methods. Whereas crossmodal correspondences are suitable for both a pragmatic and a hedonic optimization, suggesting semantic and experiential concepts to the consumers, the psychophysics is basically the discipline that measures the ability of humans to perceive given feedback, and therefore is particularly suited for the pragmatic optimization.

Crossmodal correspondences

The study of how multisensory information is coded by our brains has widely interested researchers in sensory science for many years now (Calvert et al., 2004). Interestingly, a new research trend focused on what are called crossmodal correspondences is now emerging.

The term 'crossmodal correspondence' includes a range of topics expressed in literature under different names (i.e., 'synesthetic correspondences', and 'synesthetic associations' — just to name a few). In fact, crossmodal correspondences, '...refer to a compatibility effect between attributes or dimensions of a stimulus (i.e.: an object or event) in different sensory modalities (be they redundant or not)' (Spence, 2011).

Crossmodal correspondences have often been studied by means of relatively simple mappings (or associations) between stimuli presented in modalities such as vision and audition (i.e., Marks, 2003); vision and olfaction (i.e., Demattè et al., 2006; Maric & Jacquot, 2013); touch and olfaction (i.e., Demattè et al., 2006) etc.

Crossmodal correspondences found also a large application to product design (Spence, 2012). As is not difficult to imagine, it is a thrilling concept for a designer to suggest sensation, or ideas to the consumer, by means of 'mere' sensory stimulation. In some extent, crossmodal correspondence represents everything that design is about, and what the design shares with art: to express your own aesthetic sense and elicit in the consumer, by means of a sensoria experience, concepts and ideas. More recently, crossmodal correspondences have been applied to product design assessing their effect by means of experiments (see Schifferstein & Spence, 2007, for a review), and the effect of the packaging on the perception of the product itself (see Spence & Piqueras-Fiszman, 2012; Piqueras-Fiszman et al., 2013, for a review).

For example, Piqueras-Fiszman and Spence (2012a) recently investigated the influence that the weight of food containers, cutlery, and packaging has on feelings of satiety (before and after tasting the food, in their case, a yogurt), and/or on the perception of density of the food itself. These researchers reported that increasing the weight (of the packaging/plate ware/cutlery) influenced the perceived density of the product contained inside (see Spence & Piqueras-Fiszman, 2012b, for a review). These researchers also confirmed the weight-density illusion originally proposed by Piqueras-Fiszman et al. (2011). The participants in this study also expected the contents of a heavier container to be more satiating than when exactly the same contents were presented in a visually-

identical, but physically lighter, container. A number of other studies have focused on investigating the visual features of products and their containers. The appearance of the product and the colour of its packaging also exert a significant influence on consumer perception, behaviour, and preferences (i.e., Marshall et al., 2006).

In fact, studies in crossmodal correspondences are versatile and applicable both to the pragmatic and hedonic characteristics of the product. However, all the studies on crossmodal correspondences have been carried out basing on the intuition of designers and psychologists rather than following a systematic methodology able to spot which aspect of the product to enhance or optimize utilizing this sensory science. This methodology is able to direct the studies on the sensory characteristics of the product onto the important features of the product itself, in order to enhance both its pragmatic and hedonic characteristics.

Psychophysics

Psychophysics has been used for many years in order to test the resolution of our perceptual systems (in particular, hearing, haptics, and vision). For decades the main objective of psychophysics has been the establishment of perceptual thresholds that could describe the sensitivity of our sensory systems under different conditions (Purghé, 1997). In particular, psychophysics focuses on the definition of absolute limen (AL), and differential limen (DL). AL is defined as the minimum level of stimulation needed to elicit a sensation in a person. DL instead refers to the minimum difference needed to be presented to the person for them to be able to distinguish between two stimuli of the same kind that appear to vary in intensity. Another main objective of psychophysics is the creation of scales regarding human sensations. Characteristic of such scales is the fact that they connect a given physical variable to a sensoria or psychological variable.

As a matter of fact, psychophysics assumes a great importance when it comes to assess the pragmatic characteristics of the design product. Especially in cases such as interface and new technology device design, it is important for the designer to be sure that all the feedback is clearly perceivable by the users. On the other hand it might be useful for the designer to know the limits of the human perception, in order to avoid wasting effort and time in designing oversensitive devices (see Gallace & Spence, 2014).

According to classic psychophysics, there are different methods to assess AL and DL. In particular, in the computer-based version of the methodology, some of the principal methods are described, and the experimental procedure to investigate thresholds and the formulas to compute them are enlisted. In particular, the methods of limits, adjustments, and constant stimuli are exposed.

Psychophysics has been used to validate or obtain information that can guide the design of devices and interfaces (i.e., Tan, Durlach, Reed, & Rabinowitz, 1999). Furthermore, in these cases, the performed studies were isolated, rather than framed as

part of a design methodology. The use of psychophysics in the methodology presented here is instead well defined. Thanks to the Interaction Study phase, the designer can find which kinds of sensorial feedback the user pays more attention to, and under which condition the user will need to perceive them. Subsequently, the threshold measures will serve as concrete guidelines to design/optimize that feedback.

CASE STUDY

Several case studies have been developed using the methodology reported above. In the following section, a case study will be exposed as an example to illustrate the efficacy and the functioning of the present methodology. More specifically, in the present case study, the design question was related to the concept of efficacy, and in particular asked how to augment the perceived expected efficacy of a liquid soap at the moment of purchase. It is important to note that the same case study could serve as an example also for a hedonic optimization procedure as well. In fact, the procedure would not change with a different design question (i.e., how to augment the perceived pleasantness of the product). In the case study outlined, we performed a Conjoint Analysis experiment in order to find out the sensory attributes related to the idea of efficacy in the liquid soap. We subsequently performed an experiment to boost the perceived efficacy of the soap by means of crossmodal correspondences.

Design question: In this case the design question we were asked to answer was: How to augment the perceived expected efficacy of the product when the user has to choose it from the shelves of a supermarket? In order to answer to this question we first performed a screening of the literature on crossmodal correspondence applied to hygiene, body care, and bath product, focusing specifically on soaps and body lotions finding, as reported in the literature (i.e., Churchill et al., 2009), that the role of olfaction in product evaluation was crucial.

Interaction study: In the second phase, in order to study the perception of the user in terms of efficacy, a conjoint analysis experiment was performed on twenty healthy participants (twelve male), aged between nineteen and thirty-four years (mean of twenty-six years). A set of twelve identical soap bottles (Figure four) were painted in one of three different colors: White (low color intensity), pink (medium color intensity), and red (high color intensity). Two different quantities of perfume were added to the soaps contained in the bottles. The lower concentration consisted of three drops of a strong perfume essence ("Dragon's Blood"), whereas the higher concentration consisted of the addition of seven drops per bottle. The essence was thoroughly mixed with the soap in the bottle, and the weight of half the bottles was increased by inserting a 100-gram weight into the soap container. The task of the participant was to interact with each bottle (lifting it, smelling the content, etc.), and subsequently rate the expected efficacy of each bottle of soap using a Borg CR100 response scale (Borg, 2007).

Figure 4: Stimuli used in the case study

An Analysis Of Variance (ANOVA), that included weight, fragrance, and color as predictors was applied to the data. According to this analysis, the soap contained in the heavier bottles was rated as having a higher expected efficacy ($p < .01$). Moreover, although there was not a significant effect of bottle color saturation, or fragrance intensity on perceived efficacy, the mean expected efficacy for the bottles with the lower fragrance intensity was lower than that for the bottles with the higher fragrance intensity, and the p value concerning that factor was relatively low. Therefore, the factors to consider relevant when the user had to judge the expected efficacy of a product were considered to be fragrance intensity and weight. Therefore the third phase of the optimization procedure was applied.

Sensory boost: In this phase a sensory experiment was performed, in order to exploit the phenomenon of crossmodal correspondences augmenting the perceived weight and the perceived fragrance of the bottle's contents using sensory signals coming from different sensory channels. The senses of taste and hearing were not considered, since it is unlikely that these two senses could be used in a market-like environment. For this study, the same stimuli and procedure of the conjoint analysis were used. Participants were asked to rate with the same modality the Borg CR100 scale, but this time on the perceived intensity of the fragrance. Moreover, participants were also asked to give an estimation of the weight of each bottle.

To test for any effects of color, fragrance intensity, and product weight on the perceived intensity of the liquid soap contained within the bottles, an analysis of variance (ANOVA; $\alpha = 0.05$) was performed on the data ($p < .001$). Post-hoc comparison (Bonferroni corrected: $\alpha = .05/3$) revealed statistically significant differences in the perceived intensity of the fragrance of the soap, as a function of the color of the bottle (all $ps < .001$).

In particular, the liquid soap presented in the red bottles was perceived (on average) as having a fragrance that was significantly stronger than that of the other bottles. That is, the participants rated the fragrance sniffed from red bottles as being 16% more intense than the fragrance sniffed from the pink bottles, and as being 44% more intense than the fragrance sniffed from the white bottles. Meanwhile, the fragrance of

the soap contained in the pink bottles was rated as 30% more intense than the perfume of the soap contained in the white bottles. As expected, the bottles containing the more intense fragrance were rated as having a smell that was 30% stronger than the bottles containing the weaker fragrance ($p < .001$). Interestingly, the liquid soap contained in the heavier bottles was also rated, on average, as having a fragrance that was 15% more intense than the soap contained in the lighter bottles ($p < .05$). No statistically significant effects of the interactions between the considered factors were observed.

An ANOVA ($\alpha = 0.05$) was also performed in order to test for the effects of color, fragrance intensity, and weight on the perceived weight of the bottles. No effect of the other sensory modalities was found on the estimated weight. Indeed, the only effect that was documented related to the weight inserted into the bottles.

Conclusion: In the present case study the ability to enhance the expected efficacy of liquid bath soap was examined and augmented by means of the proposed methodology. In the interaction phase of the study, the characteristics of the product important in determining its expected efficacy (that were: fragrance and weight) were highlighted. Subsequently, a sensory study was performed on fragrance and weight, in order to boost these two characteristics of the product by means of crossmodal correspondences. Results reported that changing the color of the bottles and augmenting their weight would augment the perceived fragrance, and as a consequence the perceived efficacy of the product. In fact by only acting on the packaging, without modifying the content of the bottle, designers would be able to reach an optimized product.

CONCLUSIONS

The present work exposes a methodology aimed at supporting designers in enhancing the product experience by means of experimental methods. In particular the methodology comprises a first phase in which the designer clarifies the design question expressed by the client. In a second stage, the interaction between user and product is assessed, adopting one or more experimental tools, which are reviewed in the computer-based version. In this way, the designer will understand the product's most important characteristics related to the design question. Finally, a sensory optimization experiment is performed in order to enhance and improve the product experience by means of cross modal correspondences or threshold measurements. A case study is also provided to show how the methodology works in practice.

A further aim of this methodology can be seen as to understand, revise, and finally expose methods and theories connected with the last two phases, in order to allow the designer to choose the methods to apply during the design process. Eighteen methods have been already listed in the Interaction Study section, plus three methods that have been inserted into the psychophysical phase.

It is noteworthy that both the second and third phases of the methodology require basic statistical skills. However, it is common for the designer to work in a multidisciplinary environment, where information from the market is often considered and analyzed by means of statistical tests. We assume therefore that it is not hard nowadays for a designer to deal with statistical data and results, maybe while asking for a little help. Moreover, the statistical skills required by the majority of the methods are basic, and there are plenty of computer programs able to perform them in a semi-automatic way.

Further objectives see the computer-based version of the methodology made available online, and editable by whoever is willing to add a new method or useful information to it.

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FEELER REFLECTION GAME

A CASE STUDY ON A DESIGN GAME FOR PARTICIPATORY DESIGN

Eva Durall, Teemu Leinonen
Aalto University School of Arts, Design and Architecture
✉ eva.durall@aalto.fi, teemu.leinonen@aalto.fi
Juan Fernando González
University of Barcelona, Faculty of Fine Arts
✉ gonzalezgiraldo@ub.edu

ABSTRACT

The paper explores the potential of design games as a method for developing empathetic understandings between designers and end users. With this aim, we have developed the *Feeler Reflection Game*, a board game designed to serve the contextual inquiry and early participatory design sessions of a design research looking for solutions to help people reflect on their well-being and learning. The text includes a description of the game design process, as well as an analysis of the game's use in a workshop. The case study confirms findings of earlier studies demonstrating the power of storytelling, personas, and scenarios in design. Furthermore, the case study shows that by playing the design game, the participants were able to identify themselves with the concept design and with the main situations of use. We conclude that the game acted as a boundary object that allowed participants and designers to engage in an empathic and productive dialogue.

KEYWORDS: *Design Games, Participatory Design, Empathic Design, Design Methods, User-centered Design*

INTRODUCTION

In Participatory Design (PD) tradition, people who are expected to use the product or service have a special role. First of all, because they are experts in the field in which designers want to approach; and secondly, because in the end, the users are the ones who will benefit or suffer from the final design. For this reason, designers must ensure that the solutions provided are truly beneficial and sustainable. In order to come up with innovations that respond to the users' needs and expectations in a certain context, it is necessary to incorporate the users' insights into the design process. The Scandinavian tradition has strongly advocated democratic processes within the design project through the inclusion of points of views, as well as by offering participants the means to understand the design process and have a true impact on it. According to the Scandinavian tradition, users have the right to intervene in the design process.

PD has had an influence in areas such as HCI, user-centered design, interaction design, and information systems development. Key background assumptions and methods of the PD

approach, such as the right of people to take part in decisions dealing with their living and working conditions, the awareness of the benefits that users' insights can bring to the design process, as well as the value of techniques like mock-ups, low-fi prototypes, workshops...etc., have been widely adopted (Bannon & Ehn, 2012).

In design, especially in user-centered design, empathy has been stressed as a way to achieve a better understanding of the user and the user's experience. Through empathic design (Koskinen et al., 2003), designers try to get closer to the lives and experiences of end users, in order to design a product or service that truly meets the users' needs. The PD tradition has emphasized mutuality and reciprocity (e.g. Muller, 2003) as means to improve communication and collaboration. The recognition of everyone's knowledge and the possibility to learn from each other are some of the traits that Muller attributes to hybrid spaces, situations that enable new relationships and understandings (2003). It is interesting to consider how different methods in PD, such as workshops, stories, photos, dramas, and games, among others, contribute to this hybridity. Games seem to be a promising option for developing shared

ownership, questioning assumptions, achieving mutual learning, synthesizing new ideas, negotiating, and co-creating. In PD, playing games with the end users may improve communication and provide not only new information and space for participants to contribute to the design, but also a shared space for emphatic, communal, and situated learning.

To study the potential of games in PD, we have designed several board games for various design cases. The games are custom made, since the idea is to design a game for each specific design case. In this paper, we present the *Feeler Reflection Game*, a board game designed to serve the contextual inquiry and early participatory design sessions of a design research looking for solutions to help people reflect on their well-being and learning. We describe the experience of designing the game and analyze the use of the game as a participatory practice that enables researchers and designers to develop an empathetic understanding of their participants.

In the following section, we present design games as a research technique for supporting empathy in the design process. We continue describing and analyzing the *Feeler Reflection Game*, a case in which a design game was used with the aim of augmenting understanding about the users' contexts, needs, and expectations. In the discussion, we defend the key role of design games for creating a playful and relaxed atmosphere that facilitates communication and collaboration. We conclude by considering design games as boundary objects that facilitate an empathic understanding between users and designers.

DEVELOPING EMPATHY THROUGH DESIGN GAMES

In order to promote empathy during the design process, a variety of methods and tools have been developed. The Kouprie and Visser (2009) classification recognizes three main classes of techniques: (1) for research, (2) for communication, and (3) for ideation. Research techniques that aim to foster empathy are often focused on promoting direct contact between designers and users. In the PD tradition, Johansson (2005) has noted that 'User involvement enabled the development of a special kind of field studies that is much more design-oriented than traditional ethnographic studies' (2005, p.15-16). Hence, knowledge about the end users and the design context goes beyond descriptive practices, since researchers and designers seek to achieve an empathetic understanding of users' experiences. Mattelmäki (2006) points out the need for creative and collaborative methods that enable designers to develop open interpretations about the design context that will help them to develop empathy. The creative and collaborative practices can be, for instance, the use of *probes* (Gaver et al., 1999; Mattelmäki, 2006), *mock-ups* and *prototypes* (Ehn, 1988), *Make Tools* (Sanders & Dandavate, 1999), *design games* (Ehn & Sjögren, 1991; Johansson, 2005; Brandt & Messeter, 2004), *scenarios* (Binder, 1999), or *drama* (Brandt and Grunnet, 2000).

Some researchers see a lot of similarities between design and games. These are, for instance, their social component,

evolving, and rule-based nature. According to Salen and Zimmerman (2004, p.80), 'A game is a system in which players engage in an artificial conflict, defined by rules, that results in a quantifiable outcome'. In the case of design, the design problems, the available resources, participants and their roles, as well as the work processes form boundaries for the design work and define the design space in a similar way as the rules in a game define what one can do in it. According to Vaajakallio (2012), games have been used in design for design research (Habraken & Gross, 1988), for building design competences among design students (Iversen & Buur, 2002), for empowering users, like in the 'layout kit' developed by Ehn and Sjögren (1991), and for engaging multiple stakeholders (Brandt & Messeter, 2004). Design games can be tools to define the design space. According to Botero (2013, p.59), a design space can be understood as 'the space of potentials that the available circumstances afford for the emergence of new designs at multiple levels'. Building on this definition, playing a design game can be a tool to intensify the relations among people, things, and activities. When playing a game, end users, designers, and stakeholders in general, can explore different alternatives and make collective design decisions. This transforms and expands the initially given design space by increasing empathy among participants.

Including empathic thinking in design can be a way to find inspiration and creativity about future products or design solutions (Steen et al., 2007); in other words, to broaden the design space. In PD, design games have gained popularity as a method for designers and users to jointly explore design issues on a conceptual level — to involve users in creative activity (Brandt, 2006). From this angle, explorative design games support formatting design dialogues that 'engage intended users, various stakeholders and the design team in joint inquiry into existing practice and participatory design of possible futures' (Brandt, 2006, p.61). Exploratory design games are a specific type of design game named by Brandt and Messeter (2004) that place great emphasis on engaging multiple stakeholders (Vaajakallio, 2012). Brandt (2006) distinguishes four types of exploratory design games: (1) games to conceptualize designing, (2) exchange perspective games, (3) negotiation and work-flow-oriented design games, and (4) scenario-oriented design games.

The capacity of games for creating stories, in which participants step in and play a role, helps to dissolve hierarchies, which in turn promotes a more relaxed participation. In this regard, Kronqvist et al. (2012, p.4) highlight 'Games introduce a way for engaging the participants in a mode of storytelling through the use of certain rules, material props, and visual aesthetics that set the context'. The use of storytelling in games enables players to develop an empathic connection with the situations presented. As Costikyan (2000, p.51) claims, players create experiences when participating in a game, and these generate emotional responses. 'And because a player is involved in the creation of the experience, because the experience of play is at least as much his product as that of the game designer, the emotions he feels can affect him much more deeply than the surface, empathic response you feel when viewing or reading

about characters in a story'. Design games can take advantage of storytelling as a strategy to produce empathy among participants and, therefore, allow for a better and deeper understanding of the design concept and its challenges.

From the design perspective, storytelling has proved useful for designers. The use of techniques such as the creation of personas, scenarios, storyboards, and role-playing has been applied to help designers gain understanding and empathy towards users' experiences (Buchenau & Suri, 2000). As Fulton Suri states (2003, p.52), empathic design aims at 'achieving greater awareness, an extended imagination and sensitivity to another person's world in a powerfully memorable way'. Building on these contributions, we can claim that games create an enjoyable atmosphere that allows equal communication and

facilitates sharing experiences between participants. Smooth communication and willingness to collaborate are key conditions for understanding how people experience things and for developing empathy with their world visions.

FEELER REFLECTION GAME

The Feeler Reflection Game is a board game, where the players are invited on a journey by moving from one square to another in turns. In the game, each player picks a predefined persona from six options. The players' personas are all university students, aged 19 to 23, that have different motivations for self-monitoring (Table 1).

	<p>JENNA – 23-year-old medical student</p> <p>Jenna has suffered from migraines and insomnia since she was a teenager. Throughout time, she has learned to listen to her body in order to prevent the headaches and the insomnia. She likes to experiment and find new ways of doing things.</p>
	<p>PEKKA – 19-year-old industrial design student</p> <p>Pekka enjoys testing new gadgets and mobile apps. For him, understanding how something works is a challenge he can't let go. Once he has solved a problem, he completely forgets it. He is quite dispersed, and quite often he has problems staying attentive for long periods of time.</p>
	<p>MING – 19-year-old computer science student</p> <p>There's nothing Ming enjoys more than work that's done well. She is very organized but has a terrible memory. For this reason, she writes lists of things to do, so she can make sure she doesn't miss anything. Her ability for prioritizing is appreciated when leading group projects.</p>
	<p>SAMIR – 22-year-old business student</p> <p>Samir likes to think that everything has a solution; it's just a matter of having enough data. He also thinks that everyone has the limits one wants to have. He is ambidextrous, and when he was a child he was diagnosed as dyslexic. He is not afraid of mistakes, and he enjoys trying new things.</p>
	<p>OLGA – 20-year-old communication student</p> <p>Olga makes great use of social media. She has traveled a lot, and she likes to stay in touch with all her friends. Feeling part of a group is very important to her. Over the last two years, she has experienced some tiredness and mild depression during the winter term.</p>
	<p>TIMO – 21-year-old art student</p> <p>Timo is very social, but sometimes he wants to have some time for himself. From his point of view, one should focus on the present and experience it with all the senses. Even if he makes use of digital technologies, he is quite skeptical about its benefits.</p>

Table 1. Feeler Reflection Game persona descriptions

Source: Feeler Reflection Game

The goal of the game is to change the behavior of the persona each player is playing in order to improve the personas' learning performance. For this, players need to reach the last square of the game board. Although the game is not competitive, all players should go through all the squares of the board to earn a minimum of eighteen points, which will enable them to move to the final square. The game has ten squares, each one requiring that players perform a specific action. The actions in the squares are:

Square 1: Choose a persona. Decisions are made based on the image displayed in the pawn. Once the selection is made, players receive the character card corresponding to their persona and have some time for carefully examining the profile information.

Square 2: Define the persona degree of motivation for engaging in self-monitoring. On each of the character cards, the persona's level of motivation for improving their well-being is expressed quantitatively. On this square, participants have the opportunity to increase the number initially given by rolling the dice and adding the points earned.

Square 3: Select the type of data to monitor. Players choose from a pre-made list that includes monitoring: a) learning performance and sleep, b) learning performance and physical activity, and c) learning performance, sleep, and physical activity.

Square 4: Define a research question. Participants need to write a concrete question that they can answer through the data. The aim is to gain a better understanding of the persona's condition and, therefore, to be able to find a solution.

Square 5: Pick a device for data collection. Players can choose between the following options for gathering their data: a) by hand, b) mobile app, c) mobile in-built sensor, or d) wearable device. Each device is numerically evaluated according to several features dealing with battery, data management, comfort, cost, and data accuracy. All devices award the same amount of points, but are differently distributed depending on the tool strengths and weaknesses. Players have to make their choice, taking into consideration their character's idiosyncrasy. On

this square, participants receive a sticker containing the information about the data collection device chosen that they have to attach to their character's card.

Square 6: Collect the data. In this square, players must choose between two card piles: one dedicated to challenges dealing with data collection, whereas the other one is dedicated to positive aspects. Players roll the dice and, depending if the result is even or odd, they take a card from a different pile. If the player gets a challenge card dealing with a particular feature, some points are subtracted from the total amount assigned to the device. In the opposite case, if the player takes a card focused on the advantages, some points are added.

Square 7: Choose a data visualization type. Participants can visualize their data using: a) a bubble chart, b) a line chart, c) a radar chart, d) a metaphor, or e) a dashboard. Once they have made their selection, they get a sticker with the representation of the data visualization type.

Square 8: Analyze the data. Again, on this square, there are two card piles. In one pile, cards refer to positive aspects of data visualization and give points. In the other pile, cards are focused on data visualization challenges. If players take one of those cards, they get zero or negative points. Players decide from which pile they can take the card by rolling the dice.

Square 9: Determine the readiness for a change. Players count the total amount of points earned during the game in order to determine if they can move to the next square. Those who get more than eighteen points are supposed to have enough motivation, data, and insights to modify their habits and, therefore, reach the last square. Those who haven't gained the necessary amount of points to access the last square must remain in this position.

Square 10: End of the game. Players who reach this square have successfully completed the game.

The game pieces include:

- Pawns with a printed representation of the characters available for players.

Figure 1. Images of the design game used during the contextual inquiry of the Feeler prototype.

- Character cards containing the personas' descriptions, in which players can annotate their game choices.
- Stickers of the devices for data collection and the data visualization types.
- Data collection and data visualization cards identifying challenges and possibilities.
- Dice. Although players are expected to consciously make some decisions during the game, on some occasions, they just roll the dice and this determines the consequences.

In the *Feeler Reflection Game*, each pawn is different and is associated with a character card that includes a description, motivation level to solve the particular problem he/she faces, as well as some empty fields that players need to fill in as the game advances (figure 2). The characters portrayed in the game are personas built according to the research developed by Gimpel et al. (2013), as well as to interviews made with potential end users.

The aesthetics of the *Feeler Reflection Game* borrow from traditional game boards. The selected colors and materials seek to recreate a playful, enjoyable environment that arouses players' curiosity. From the beginning, it was considered important to make participants feel confident and willing to experiment. The use of vivid colors, along with simple and roundish shapes, creates a safe environment, which is visually appealing. In order to stress the storytelling side, it was decided not to use photographs and, instead, adopt an aesthetic based on hand-drawing for the characters and icons for the rest of the game materials.

ANALYSIS OF FEELER REFLECTION GAME INTERACTIONS

The *Feeler reflection Game* has been created in the framework of a design research looking for solutions to help people to reflect on their well-being and learning. The game is used to elaborate on a design concept called Feeler, a software and service that

is able to visualize learning performance and well-being based on data collected from online learning services and tools capturing physical activities, such as movement, exercise, nutrition, and sleeping. The aim of *Feeler* is to encourage people to reflect on their lifestyle and its impact on their learning capabilities.

The *Feeler reflection game* has been developed for a series of workshops of the *Feeler* prototype. In the following, we focus on the latest, which was conducted with five graduate students of art and design. The three design research objectives of the game and playing it with various participants were to:

1. Develop empathic understanding of participants' practices and needs related to self-monitoring,
2. Share and explore the design challenges with the participants related to reflection and behavior change,
3. Obtain feedback and validate initial design concepts that are based on previous research.

Participants started the workshop by playing the *Feeler reflection game*, lasting approximately 45 minutes. The game was followed by a discussion about several issues dealing with the prototype design, such as motivation, data collection, data visualization, and how to better support behavior change. The data gathered during the game for further analysis included a video recording of the session, participants' character cards on which they annotate their game actions, and the design researcher's notes.

In order to infer to what extent playing a game helped participants develop an empathic understanding of the design goals and challenges, qualitative content analysis was used as a method for analyzing the data. Qualitative content analysis is, according to Sandelowski (2000, p.338), 'a dynamic form of analysis of verbal and visual data that is oriented toward summarizing the informational contents of that data'. The codes used for categorizing the data were generated from the data in the course of the study. In this case, the codes that show an empathic understanding of the situations presented are identification, role-playing, connection with real-life experiences, and creation of a relaxed atmosphere.

Figure 2. Images of the *Feeler Reflection Game* character cards and pawns.

At the beginning of the game, players picked their character based on the pawns' images. Despite the lack of information, participants' choices showed some sort of identification with the character, mainly based on physical resemblance.

Player 3: 'I... uhhmm.... Actually I want to be this one (referring to the character). My hair use to be like that'.

Transcript 1. Player picks the character she would use during the game.

After the character selection, players received a characters' card in which they could read a short description of their characters' traits and motivation for engaging in self-monitoring. This background information helped them to make some decisions and to engage in role-playing.

Player 1: 'I want to get feedback if what I'm doing is good for my health... because I have some mild depressions in winter... and also I feel quite tired so I want to monitor my sleep to see if I can find some relationship between... I don't know yet'.

Transcript 2. Player tries to define a research question to answer through self-monitoring.

One aspect that indicates the players' identification with their characters is the use of first person when referring to their game persona. In some cases, players referred to their character using first person at all times, therefore, showing a high level of involvement in the role-play; whereas in others, they only used third person or alternated between both forms.

Player 5: 'Pekka has this problem of keeping attention, so then, how long I sleep, but also how I... So, whether if my physical activity and my sleep impact my attention span'.

Transcript 3. Player combines the use of third and first person when talking about her game character.

Another aspect that shows players' empathy towards their characters deals with the connection between real-life and game decisions. In this regard, it is interesting to note that, before playing the *Feeler Reflection Game*, some of the players had experimented with self-monitoring of different aspects of their habits. Curiously, in the game, rather than experimenting with new ways of self-monitoring, some of them replicated what they had tried in real-life.

Player 2: 'Yes it was. In my case, I was monitoring sleep in the same way I was acting in the game'.

Transcript 4. Player recognizes she self-monitored herself in the same way as in the game.

Despite that self-identification with the characters only happened while playing the game, we can infer that it allowed for an empathic understanding of the personas and scenarios dealing with self-monitoring. From our point of view, role-playing and self-identification contributed to a meaningful and situated discussion about the design challenges of self-monitoring tools.

The use of a game allowed combining formal and informal registers. This was noticeable in the case of the facilitator, who used a more formal register when explaining about the research aims and the instructions of the game and a more informal one while playing. During the game, the use of storytelling techniques enabled the facilitator to abandon the academic register and get into the situation by making jokes, naming players by their characters' names and thus creating a playful and relaxed atmosphere. In this regard, the use of humor contributed to liberate players from prejudices and spontaneously express themselves.

Figure 3. Workshop participants playing the *Feeler Reflection Game*.

Despite the fact that the game board presented a linear timeline highlighting main moments in the process of self-monitoring, participants felt confident enough to bring other topics to the discussion, which were not initially foreseen, such as reward systems or other types of data they would like to monitor, such as stress, weather conditions, or nutrition.

At some point, they also considered it necessary to rearrange the order of the board squares, since, from their point of view, some decisions, such as the definition of the research question, should be approached at the very beginning of the process. The fact that each square on the board was independent from the others enabled the rearrangement of the squares to be fast and easily. In this regard, the visualization of information, either by noting down information on the characters' cards, or by altering the initially given order of the squares, contributed to maintaining the focus and discussing the issues in detail.

During the discussion, participants reflected about the use of a game as a way for presenting academic research. Although they enjoyed playing the *Feeler Reflection Game*, from their

point of view, it was necessary to improve the game playability. According to the participants' comments, the game was too short and offered few opportunities to make decisions that had consequences later on. Since the game was intended to be used at the beginning of the workshop as a way to present the research topics, it was considered important to keep a time limit. However, according to participants, these initial constraints are not so important, and stress should be placed on creating opportunities for players to meaningfully intervene.

DISCUSSION

The Feeler Reflection Game was designed during the contextual inquiry of the *Feeler* work-in-progress prototype. According to Leinonen (2008, 2010), contextual inquiry is an initial stage of the research-based design process that consists in an exploration of the socio-cultural context of the design. During the contextual inquiry, designers may use rapid ethnographic methods, such as participant observation and user interviews, for exploring design situations and defining design challenges. Although design games have been highly used in co-design sessions in PD (Brandt 2006; Vaajakallio, 2012), we consider that they are powerful tools to use in the early stages of the design process in order to create a productive dialogue (Kronqvist et al., 2012; Vaajakallio, 2012).

Considering that the *Feeler Reflection Game* was used as a strategy for presenting end users' different personas and initial scenarios of the use of the future design, it shares some characteristics with the scenario-oriented design games defined by Brandt (2006). According to this author, 'enacted scenario construction can be viewed as an exploratory design game because it involves a play with props, takes place within a pre-defined location, is limited in time, and follows specific rules' (2006, p.59). In the *Feeler Reflection Game*, the creation of personas allowed participants to interpret a role and develop it further according to their own views. Similarly to the Brandt et al. *User Game* (2008), the *Feeler Reflection Game* aimed to create a shared image, between designers and workshop participants, of the end users, based on the field data.

The generation of scenarios in design is a well-known practice. According to Schön (1983), the creation of scenarios is a design technique that helps to restructure a design situation and provides new insights. The scenarios presented in the *Feeler Reflection Game* described a particular interpretation of a QS tool use situation, but incomplete and open to negotiation (Carroll, 2000). The actions taken and decisions made by players when playing the game contributed to recreating and completing the scenario of use.

Player 1: 'I could do the same thing (noting down the data by hand as another player decided to do), but I'm a computer science student (referring to the persona she picked), so I use technology (a smart phone with an built-in sensor)'.

Transcript 5. Player explains why her character makes a certain decision.

The game board layout offered participants a comfortable environment in which they could already advance certain aspects, such as the presence of rules and the existence of a certain path, among others (Johansson, 2005). Furthermore, as Kronqvist et al. (2012) highlight, the game board acted as a design medium with a double function: presenting information to participants and engaging them to freely communicate personal experiences and views. The game board was also a great resource for guiding and informing the discussion about the concept design of the future prototype.

The game materials were used as 'things-to-think-with' (Pappert, 1980; Brandt, 2006) that participants used to analyze the situation and give new meanings to it. The game offered a common language that helped structuring the argumentation and exchange of people's views (Brandt & Messeter, 2004). In this regard, as Brandt (2006) and Kronqvist et al. (2012) outline, game materials can function as boundary objects (Star, 1989), since they support dialogue between different disciplines and interests.

Finally, we would like to present the design of games as a design work (Johansson, 2005). The construction of a design game requires designers to structure and define what would be at the center of the design process. In the case of the *Feeler Reflection Game*, a lot of effort was put into presenting previous research results in a suggestive and playful way, so participants would feel comfortable to freely express themselves and contribute to the concept design. In this regard, the game design had its own process. A couple of weeks before the workshop, a low-fi prototype of the game was tested, and some aspects were redesigned according to the feedback provided. The experience of creating a game was an interesting exercise for enabling designers to identify with end users and for improving communication techniques with them.

CONCLUSIONS

In this article, we present design games as a useful strategy in PD to develop an empathic understanding of end users from early stages of the design, concretely during the contextual inquiry. Design games act as boundary objects that provide an engaging and pleasurable experience that facilitates players' free expression, and in which participants' concerns are taken into consideration.

According to our experience, design games work in two different ways. In the case of users, the game players, the game offers a unique environment for presenting previous research results, such as scenarios and personas through storytelling techniques. This way, players can easily identify themselves with the personas and scenarios and contribute to the research by helping to envision future practices in design.

From our perspective, as designers and researchers, creating a design game requires putting ourselves in the end users' position in order to present a situation that stimulates end users' communicability and creativity. In this regard, the game works as an example of empathic design since it seeks to find

inspiration in end users by empathizing with them. Furthermore, the game works as workshop agenda, since it contributes to presenting the design topics and creating an experience on which players can discuss later. Considering all the above-stated information, design games offer great opportunities for developing mutual learning and empathy among end users and designers.

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VISUAL WORKFLOWS FOR DESIGN PROJECT KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT

Jaime Rivera, Yassine Abouhazim*, Laura Mattis, Stan Ruecker, Patricia Wang
 Illinois Institute of Technology. Institute of Design. Chicago, Illinois 60654, USA
 *Illinois Institute of Technology, Armour College of Engineering. Chicago, Illinois 60616, USA
 ✉ Jaime@id.iit.edu, yabouhaz@hawk.iit.edu, lmattis@id.iit.edu, sruecker@id.iit.edu, patricia@id.iit.edu

ABSTRACT

This paper presents the findings of research into a digital learning knowledge management tool that uses an interactive surface to manipulate a design project in multiple stages. The research aim was to understand how designers might replace the traditional model of one device per person and use digital space as an alternative for analyzing data collaboratively. The research involved using one device for multiple users, including multi-gesture and navigability options to organize data and learning that were generated by team dynamics. Two different tests were implemented: a concept test about the general idea and a usability test with different groups of designers, to examine team dynamics. In the discussion section we consider how participants had problems recognizing a single device as appropriate for use in group activities, how the focus of attention in the interactive table took away some of the gestures and non-verbal communication that are common in team dynamics, how the novelty of the device created an initial exploration that was perceived as a game and how using an interactive technology as a tool created different levels of learning that affect the emotional response of participants. The paper concludes with recommendations about future implementations and some interesting patterns characterizing the use of the multi-touch gesture screen, such as the use of digital space as a way to control activities and the deliberate control of data as a way to impose a leadership.

KEYWORDS: *Collaborative design; communication; computer supported design; decision making; design activity.*

INTRODUCTION

Although there are a variety of project management tools available, designers are notorious for their unwillingness to employ them in anything but the most rudimentary fashion (e.g. Bernardes forthcoming). One of the barriers to adoption is the essential non-linearity of the design process, where the iterative return to previous stages of the project is typical rather than exceptional. In this study, we created a prototype for knowledge management in design projects, based on the foursquare model of research, analysis, synthesis and implementation, superimposed on an X-axis running from understanding the paper layout to making, and a Y-axis running from the real to the abstract (Figure 1). Recognizing that each of these phases needs to be ready at hand, our touch surface prototype keeps a dynamic menu object constantly available, allowing designers occupying any position on the table to shift the display quickly from the collection of raw data, to organize it by using analysis and labeling and to achieve a final synthesis and labeling protocol. We also provide a simple mechanism for generating linear presentation materials for use outside the design team proper. The design of the

prototype was informed by interviews with seven design managers at five different firms. Our user study of the prototype involved two different tests, a usability test of the working prototype with 12 design students and a concept test with a "Wizard of Oz" prototype, involving five design managers

Figure 1. The underlying model for our design management prototype. Diagram by Kim Erwin.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In product development, there are two types of project management styles: emergent and planned [4]. The planned project management style is suited to clearly defined problems, where managers provide discipline, set direction, and optimize for efficiency. The former, emergent, style is better suited to ambiguous problems, where managers enable their subordinates to be creative and flexible and to improvise solutions. According to Lewis, managers do not solely practice one style, but rather combine and alternate between both methods. While the planned management style relies heavily on time as a key measure, the emergent style heavily relies on knowledge and learning through iterations [3]. Currently, there are many similar market-available tools to facilitate the planned management style, while there are few to facilitate emergent methods. As a result, our team focused on developing tools for activities that occur in emergent product development, particularly with regards to knowledge sharing.

According to Wang [6], successful knowledge systems are heavily influenced by:

- Easy and effective methods for adding data and searching categories and indexes;
- Preferences for autocratic or consultative management styles; and
- The complexity level of the project.

Furthermore, Wang [6] suggests that there are two types of communication styles. The first involves linear, formal and vertical sharing (such as PowerPoint presentations) and the second involves informal, egalitarian sharing (such as conversations and discussions). Because both styles of communication are present within an organization, the tool that our team developed was required to support both styles and help users capture and transfer knowledge easily between the two styles and their associated contexts.

Additionally, according to Zigurs [8], technology, while good at communication, process-setting and information handling, is not adaptable to support teams in the midst of reframing and restructuring. The project management prototype developed by the team will specifically look at this assertion, as it is designed to facilitate and capture new connections between data, while still providing access to old connections developed in other stages.

Specifically, the team investigated group dynamics and leadership around control of the Multitaction table, which is designed for multiple, simultaneous users. As Yuill and Rogers [7] and Hesselmann et al. [2] contest, a number of social and cultural barriers exist that may prevent multiple users from touching the table simultaneously. Many current devices are designed for individual and single user input. In addition, social norms may also dictate who touches the table at a given time – e.g. where the leader of the group “controls the screen”. Visual limitations (i.e., the ability to see a graphic from one’s vantage point) and the physical reach of objects may also influence who touches the table at the appropriate moment.

Finally, the team also looked at the translation of natural gestures used for handling and sorting images in the physical world to the constraints of the digital touch surface. Terrenghi [5] compares the manipulation-related affordances of physical media and interactive surfaces. Similarly, the team explored the gestures and screenflows involved in sorting and surveying images, forming collections, and hiding inessential or irrelevant information.

METHODS

For the purposes of the study, the team focused particularly on individuals involved in “design thinking” who use various research and creative methods and need to collect, organize and share out information in a collaborative setting with others. The team also felt that design consultancies with multiple disciplines and competencies were solidly extreme users who typically work with a variety of visual and physical content, generated from a wide range of tools (sketches, the Adobe Creative suite, video, physical prototypes, etc.).

During the collaborative design process, team members need to create a fundamental shared understanding of design content and process as well as to capture (or document when needed) information that allows others to understand, communicate, replicate or redesign the final output [1].

While there are digital tools that exist for designers to create by themselves, few exist to help them create simultaneously in a collaborative experience. Instead, from our observations and from ethnographic interviews, design teams still resort to physical displays in their environments because these allow all members to contribute, and to move information readily.

INITIAL RESEARCH

The team interviewed designers and project managers from different firms, ranging from small to large and from consultancies to Fortune 500 companies – over a range of competencies from CPG to technology.

Findings

We began with the hypothesis that organizations struggle with project management and that current tools were inadequate to the task. However, after interviewing participants, the team realized that organizations didn’t struggle with project management because tools such as the Gantt chart have made it easy to set deadlines and show the time-based relationships between departments. Managers can easily see whether a project is off-track by comparing current team activity with the planned schedule.

However, in companies where generated knowledge and insight are the key measures of success (in fields such as emerging technologies and development work), a Gantt chart is not an effective management tool for understanding if a project is

“on track” or generating expected value. It is in this scenario that organizations and teams struggle to report project value, because they find it hard to communicate their work within the teams themselves and to key stakeholders.

One participant described the hiring of specialized staff (known as “research public relations”) to highlight key technological contributions to external partners and lobby for further research investment. This allows technologists in the R&D division to focus on their research problems and not on communicating the value and progress of their work.

The team found that design managers and consultants particularly struggle with this problem in their role as client liaisons. Specifically, designers rely on the vertical space and the environment around them to manage, organize and share their knowledge internally.

- In contrast to digital tools, where teams rely on one person to move data in a turn-like fashion, posting to vertical surfaces is democratic: everyone is allowed to contribute and rearrange data.
- Vertical space also passively communicates the team’s progress to outside participants. Picture-filled boards communicate that the team has just completed the research phase while boards filled with page layouts denote a team that is preparing documents or presentations.

While teams opt to use their physical space to manage their data they struggle with transferring all of their digital data to the physical world. This means tediously printing out hundreds of research photographs and creating extensive paper snippets of interview transcripts or secondary research papers.

Similarly, when designers need to communicate their final work, they must convert all of those physical assets back to a digital format, usually a PowerPoint or PDF deck for their client, so the information can travel throughout the client organization. While the data might be stored in a shared location on a server or cloud service, designers still need to find all of the digital assets for their physical counterparts.

Even with walls or boards covered with data and recorded by photographs, there is never enough space for everything and designers must rely on their own documentation habits to remember design decisions. Their photographs of data clusters aren’t searchable or easily retrievable, allowing to track decisions they’ve made or patterns they’ve seen.

Additionally, at the end of the project, it is common for companies to save their digital files, but only a few store the physical information in archive systems that retain a mix of digital and tangible information. In trying to access the archives the experience is chaotic, and retrieving a specific stage of the project requires all the data to be scanned. In the same way, it is common to find information that is out of context as the learning experience of the original design team is absent.

CONCEPT TEST PROTOTYPE

In response to the feedback of our interviewees, we designed a tool that was intended to manage this information digitally through a unique use of environment, space and collaboration. Using these design principles, the team developed a concept prototype of a digital knowledge management tool

Figure 2: Concept, “Wizard of Oz” Prototype. Screen 1 = User setup. Screen 2 = Loading data. Screen 3 = Creating clusters. Screen 4 =Presentation layout display mode.

in Apple Keynote for the multi-touch Multitaction table in order to help design managers organize and share their data. Similarly to the current vertical space environment, the tool is designed to be orthogonally democratic. Most functions (with the exception of the presentation function) are designed to be executed by any team member at any edge of the table surface, regardless of another team member's actions (i.e., the table is designed to be always in "multiplayer mode").

After creating a project using the table's interface, and assigning team members to the project, users can select data snippets, such as image files, video clips and text, to be loaded onto the table's surface. Upon data selection, the materials populate the table's surface in a slow, randomized display in different orientations. Items can be rotated, moved and zoomed in an effort to organize them into named sets, or "clusters". Clusters can be named, marked as important, organized temporarily in a grid structure, and copied. Important contextual information, or "insights", about the clusters can be documented via text input and attached to the cluster as an additional data snippet.

As users enter new stages of the design process they can create duplicates of the same information for reworking or the information can be progressively reduced to the most important pieces for analysis. In each stage, the same clustering actions serve as the central form of interaction with the table. When users want to communicate their work, they can switch to a visualization mode that organizes all of the data snippets, clusters and insights in a simple grid structure according to time. At any point, users can switch between stages and visualizations, and the table display is captured using auto-save functions.

User Research

We investigated three key areas with the prototype, and sought to:

1. Understand how users learn new gestures that are beyond currently accepted digital norms (swiping, double tapping, pinching, or expanding)
2. Understand the role of team dynamics and how the table can facilitate or hinder participation by team members.
3. Understand the acceptance and desirability of such a tool for the industry.

The first two questions are related to specific activities and behaviors concerning the physical prototype and the implementation of the concept in a multi-touch, collaborative environment. The third area is related to the application of the concept in the design workflow. We therefore developed two different tests. The first was a concept test covering all of the stages of the design process with a "Wizard of Oz" prototype developed in Apple Keynote. The "Wizard of Oz" prototype is an illustration of the full program concept that works only when a human being is generating the responses of the interface. In this way, the prototype interface appears to be functional, even though software programming has not been

completed. The second test, of usability, was used for testing a specific stage of the concept: a collaborative cluster exercise with an Adobe Flash-functioning prototype for testing on the Multitaction multi-touch table.

Method

The team asked four designers to review the Apple Keynote "Wizard of Oz" prototype. These designers represented two small and two large-scale design consultancies. Additionally, two of the participants were interviewed during the initial research phase. Testers were asked to respond to what they saw as the prototype was presented full-screen on the multi-touch Multitaction table provided for the concept development. Each concept test took approximately 1 hour and conversations were audio recorded.

Results

In general, the concept testers responded positively to the concept. The prototype was considered appropriate for small design teams embedded in a large corporate environment, as opposed to widespread adoption across multiple design consultancy teams. The main reason cited for this was the rigid structure of the design process stages presented in the prototype. This structure was effective for training junior design colleagues and for containing the "design mess" in a corporate environment unfamiliar with multi-color post-it notes and paper-covered walls. One participant described the prototype as, potentially, a "good project journal" for documenting the design process and rewinding through the work:

"My job is to be deeply insightful, to create really deep insights and, it's challenging. So you have to work with your information very differently. For me, I'm going back and forth between insights from observations, what's going on at a cultural level, what are the shifts in the industry, and what's a case study. I'm dealing with more types of content than just user observation content and [I'm] working back and forth".

Testers described the tool as a "data organization tool, not a storytelling tool", but the documentation might provide key support to designers in crafting their client stories. For example, one tester wanted to be able to edit insights over time and track the evolution of language or insight focuses. This documentation was another way to capture the evolution of ideas and learning processes, and how they related to data snippets.

Overall, the concept testers were concerned about data retention. The transitions between stages were described as jarring and "anxiety-inducing". Several concept testers gasped at stage changes and complained that the information had "disappeared" and that they wanted some way to review all of the screens at once.

The team was surprised that testers requested the ability to print copies of the digital screens; they wanted to print out what was happening on the table onto paper that they could surround themselves with in a physical space.

“In my gut, after you keep switching [stages], I want to be printing everything out and putting it on the wall. I have to surround myself with the stuff -- because I’m visual, there’s something about it being accessible around me. I wanna see everything at once -- I worry that flipping back and forth would hinder my process. It could be totally silly, but I’ve never worked any other way, so it makes me kinda freaked out not being surrounded by everything”.

Several of the participants admitted to having a visual and spatial memory that was disrupted by the multiple layers of digital staged information. Testers could describe their project room walls, and the distinct screens for each stage seemed to disrupt this memory aid. Testers were also confused by the uncontextualized images and text snippets:

“If I’m reacting to the images, I’m just reacting to them. If I’m trying to put it into the context of a broader story: it could mean something, but maybe it doesn’t. The trouble with still imagery is you don’t know what it’s for. When we know, then we can assign value to it and say that’s important to know. With research, you’re always looking for wonderful examples -- poignant examples of a point you see emerging”.

Not only did the testers want to include meta-data, but they wanted a way to input sketches, diagrams and annotations. One tester specifically requested “football style” drawings that could be made using a stylus or finger.

Analysis

Our concept testers repeatedly compared the concept prototype to their current working model. They are used to surrounding themselves with data by covering the walls with images, snippets, notes and post-its. They were anxious about “disappearing information” and the confusion of their visual memory, which made them disoriented. They also frequently work remotely and would, in several cases, prefer to use the table for individual work, not collaboratively. As a result, the assets of the system had more to do with documentation and having access to the data even if they were not in the same space.

USABILITY TEST

Prototype

To understand how this technology might impact on group dynamics and hierarchy, the team developed Node, a collaborative clustering prototype created in Adobe Flash for use on the multi-touch Multitaction table by groups of designers.

The clustering program in the digital experience allows users to drag, scale, and cluster the pictures. Similar to many software products on the market, it uses standard commercially available touch gestures -- like a two-finger pull & push on the corners of the image to expand and shrink the image and one-finger drag to manipulate photographs.

Clusters are set by stacking images together then pressing and holding on the group of images. The program responds to the user’s touch by drawing a circle around a pile of images. In its final state, the cluster has a large green dot over the images that can then be moved using a one-finger drag.

Method

Twelve graduate design students, divided into four groups of three students each, were recruited from the XXX to participate in two clustering activities for one hour. The teams were comprised of a single senior student in their final year of graduate education at the Illinois Institute of technology (either their second or third year at the university), and two junior students in the first year of their graduate career. Most of the junior participants had no professional or undergraduate design experience.

The teams participated in two sorting exercises: paper clustering (the control) and digital clustering using our Node clustering prototype. Participants were asked to work together to organize images of sport or kitchen products into groups, or “clusters,”. Each team was given a unique content and exercise-order combination in an effort to limit order effects. For the prototype exercises, participants were shown how to zoom, rotate and move the content items with a single or multiple finger touch, how to lock the content together in a cluster with a press-and-hold gesture and were cautioned that clusters could only be made by one participant because of programming limitations.

The activities’ audio and visuals were documented using an aerial video camera and a secondary camera at one edge of the table. The team recorded observations throughout the two testing activities and a single team member served as activity moderator and trainer for all of the team’s testing. On completion of the second activity, participants were interviewed individually by a team researcher who asked the following questions:

1. Tell us about how easy/hard you found the activity.
2. Describe how you participated in the activity.
3. What would you change?
4. What would happen if you tried to use this table in your design work?
5. How do you think it might help you? How do you think it might hinder you?
6. What would you be frustrated with?

General Observations

The research team analyzed the paper and digital exercises in addition to the comments made in the individual interviews conducted after the group exercises. In general, we noted two roles: leaders, or senior members, and followers, or junior members. While participants were selected to amplify the dichotomy of junior and senior participants, the selected senior participants were not always the table leaders.

Forming Consensus in Both Activities

Regardless of the medium used in the activities, two types of leadership style were observed. The first style of leadership observed could be characterized as “command and control”. Junior members would start a discussion by throwing out ideas about how to cluster while the senior member would judge, strike down ideas and choose other strategies. In one test, a junior member suggested clustering the images by color and a senior member remarked, “[That] doesn’t make sense ... clearly this is content related”. As a result, the team proceeded to cluster by sport, coming up with 20 categories of data for 45 images.

The second type of leader exhibited facilitation and iteration behaviors. Users would start to cluster images together and if the team felt that images fell outside their initial construct, a single participant would stop, announce the problem, and suggest new ways of grouping images together.

Paper Cluster Exercise - Body Language and Leadership

In the paper clustering exercises participants were able to control the conversation by singling out specific pieces of data through physical gestures, pulling the data out of the second dimension and bringing it into the third dimension above the

rest of the data (Figure 3). In one case, a participant picked up an image above the table, held it up for the others to see and asked, “What is this? Where do we put it?” This grabbed the attention of the other group members, physically separated them from what they were doing, allowing them to help her and quickly reach consensus.

Paper Clustering Exercise - Team Flow

We also observed a team clear the table by picking up groups of data and shuffling them by hand, creating clear space on the table (Figure 4). This enabled them to create “thinking space” or a blank slate to help them sort the data, but it also created a personal and group data divide where the group could focus and have a conversation together based on the images on the table.

Finally, we saw that group members had subtle ways of communicating with each other during the physical exercise. For example, when one participant held a photograph in his hands for a long period of time, another participant would lean over or walk around the table to provide assistance in figuring out how it might be grouped. This naturally instigated a conversation about where to put the information and built consensus about group definitions.

Figure 3: Participants showing information to drive the conversation.

Figure 4: Participants collecting data into individual working stacks.

Digital Clustering Exercise - Contrasts in Leadership

However, in the digital exercise, users had employ deliberate actions and assert conversational dominance. This was done by enlarging images on the screen to draw people’s attention to them and controlling data access and the largest screen area (Figure 5). Junior members could no longer see the images that they were working with and were forced to focus on the enlarged image. Furthermore, we also observed senior leaders use motion to direct the attention of their junior members: leaders would touch and shake images to direct a conversation towards that specific image.

Digital Clustering Exercise - Contrasts in Team Flow

Overall, we saw that users were challenged to form consensus in the digital experience as easily as in the physical exercise. Participants were observed talking less about the data because team members were engaged in their specific activity of creating a digital cluster (Figure 6). Participants described the digital experience as “so engrossing and entertaining” but that it was hard to focus on what other group members were doing

Participants also struggled to communicate with each other non-verbally. Because of the singular participant focus, few participants made eye contact with each other and they kept

their heads down, focusing on the table and rarely looking up from the screen. Most activity took place on the table: conversations about the data, asserting conversational focus on a particular image, and gathering one’s own data for the cluster.

Because of the overall reduction in group conversation and strong focus on individual actions participants tended to move images that they didn’t know what to do with into the center with no comments or pause. As a result, participants were challenged at the end to figure out what they should do next.

Unintended Digital Disruptions & Affordances

We also noted how the prototype’s technical execution interfered with the ability of an individual to accomplish their own cluster activity. The team observed “data crashes” where participants dragged information across the table and accidentally crossed paths with another participant. Because every touched piece is brought to the front, if two participants cross information at the same time, one of them would lose the touch input and only one image would follow the intended trajectory. The other image would be “dropped” and left on the table where it was lost in the crash. Because this disrupted the intended flow, they would lose focus and move on.

Figure 5: Senior participant controlling a table conversation by enlarging content

Figure 6: Participants working individually with their heads down.

The technology also interfered with social dynamics. For the setup of the test, a double tap touch brought up the menu that retrieved the image dataset and displayed it on the table. If a team participant accidentally triggered the menu and selected a menu item, more images would be loaded onto the table, covering most, if not all, of the work completed by the team. This action was always irreversible, meaning the data had to be dealt with and could not be removed easily.

Though the research team did not intentionally plan this action, several teams triggered more data, producing surprising findings. If a team member accidentally hit the menu button and “spilled data onto the table” the group would blame the participant and make him or her liable for “cleaning up the mess”.

DISCUSSION

Social Behavior

Even though the participants in the study are heavy digital device users (smartphones, tablets, etc.), the Multi-taction table was still perceived as a single person’s device. One participant specifically asked “who’s going to control [the multi-touch table]?” inferring that only one person could move images at a time. Furthermore, in the subsequent interviews, most participants described using the device for their own personal use and not for collaborative work. According to one participant:

“If you’re working with just one surface, it feels like that one surface is yours. It’s almost disconcerting to have multiple hands on it. I think people have this one terminal, one person kind of viewpoint on things, which I think is left over from personal computing days”.

The team suggests that this might be because the prototype did not deliver an exceptional experience comparable to working with paper, or that the functional portion of the prototype shown did not have enough features to warrant the abandonment of paper. As researchers, we made the choice of having the images appear in a randomized way in order to balance the positioning of people around the table and create an egalitarian multi-user workspace.

Communication

The digital prototype was not able to facilitate natural group behavior and communication. It did not allow for eye contact between team members or for team members to seamlessly accomplish their own tasks and clusters. Because the digital prototype engages so much of the participant’s attention, the prototype became the focal point of activity and made it easy for participants to ignore the movements and behaviors of others. For this reason, conversational and behavioral leadership in the digital experience depended on deliberate and intentional actions. This included actions like enlarging photographs so that no other participant could look at any other image, or pointing and moving an image to gain attention and input.

Participants may have rejected the device for collaboration because physical space and reach dictated what they were capable of doing, and participants controlled the actions of others, restricting access to photographs by collecting all of the images on their side of the table.

Ludic Behavior

Because of the entertainment value of such a large touch-screen device, several participants “played” with it before beginning the task that was assigned to them. Fun can help break the technology barrier but it will significantly raise the users’ feature expectations as they compare their personal tablet experiences to working on the table, rather than focusing on the assigned task.

This might be an artifact of the learning process: users will understand the functions of the table better after they have explored it: testing the boundaries of what is possible and what is not. During the first minutes of each test, participants tried different gestures and tested the physics rules (i.e., participants tried to use inertia to send a picture in a given direction). It is difficult to ascertain whether the differences between physical and digital clustering come from the fact that the participants were interacting with the table for the first time but were more familiar with the clustering exercise, or if the digital experience had less to offer in terms of possibilities and thus lowered the efficiency of a work group.

Paper vs Digital: The Emotional Experience

The two different tests revealed different emotional responses on the part of participants. The paper prototype created direct communication when someone showed a picture in order to catch others’ attention or gestured by holding a piece of paper up for a long time to indicate they needed help. Both behaviors might be common in other practices and were easily understood by others.

In contrast, the levels of interaction with the digital surface when participants required attention or help involved moving the images about and changing their size. This activity had to be repeated multiple times before the other participants became aware of the problem. These interactions occurred on a trial and error basis, especially at the beginning of the activity when the way to manipulate the information was still not clear for some participants.

Concerning the digital disruptions caused by accidents with the menu, the emotional response was to blame the participant who had made the mistake instead of blaming the technology or even the group of designers who were present during the test. We observed that participants with a fast learning curve concerning the features and affordances of the interface were less tolerant of this kind of problem.

It is not our intention to generalize these situations, but at least in relation to this test it is possible to connect the different levels of learning about the interface with different emotional experiences concerning the roles of authority and tolerance

shown towards other participants who were less skilled at using digital devices. The recognition of a digital system as a tool, and not as a medium or as a facilitator, creates levels of expertise that can affect the role of the participants in a positive or negative way.

FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Concept Direction

From a user-centered point of view, the team would like to expand our concept of a workspace to include a team journal, where users could see their information and scrub from the past to the present. Because the concept prototype was presented as a number of discrete screens, users were concerned about “where their data went”.

We envisage the concept as moving towards the creation of a network of team digital devices with the table interface as a single node or touchpoint. Rather than force users to be co-located, the concept will explore how the table might bring together a centrally-located group around the table, as well as involve those who are located at a distance. This would allow users to use their own personal devices such as laptops, tablets, and smartphones -- key components of how they access and accomplish “work”.

Participants also wanted to add layers of other information, so future iterations should enable users to sketch and draw on top of the images and add “drawn” files. We imagine the addition of the third dimension could further replicate the tangible experience of working with physical materials, and make it possible for users to zoom in and out of the workspace and data snippets and be more seamless to navigate.

Research Recommendations

For further research, we would like to investigate how our concept could be an active participant, rather than a work tool. This might help shift blame towards the technology rather than social relationships, which can be frail and easily broken.

As a social tool, the table could help moderate and facilitate conversation, encouraging quiet users to speak up, and instructing all users on the specific activity, ultimately promoting individual engagement in the group context.

Finally, the team would also like to explore the table orientation by designing the screen to have a top and a bottom when posted on a vertical surface. This would further mimic the vertical space paradigm currently in use. This orientation could promote eye contact between individuals and the ability for participants to read other non-verbal communication.

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THE FUTURE OF TEXTILES SOURCING: EXPLORING THE POTENTIAL FOR DIGITAL TOOLS

Bruna Petreca

Royal College of Art, School of Design - Design Products

✉ bruna.petreca@network.rca.ac.uk

Douglas Atkinson

London College of Fashion, DISC (The Designer Manufacturer Innovation Support Centre)

✉ d.atkinson@fashion.arts.ac.uk

Dr Nadia Bianchi-Berthouze

University College London, UCL Interaction Centre (UCLIC)

n.berthouze@ucl.ac.uk

Dr Dominic Furniss

University College London, UCL Interaction Centre (UCLIC)

✉ d.furniss@ucl.ac.uk

Dr Sharon Baurley

Royal College of Art, School of Design - Design Products

✉ sharon.baurley@rca.ac.uk

ABSTRACT

Textile selection involves aspects of objective function and subjective experience. While technical assessments of textiles are extensively supported by standards and machinery that provide the industry with rigorous specifications, the more subjective characteristics remain heavily reliant on designers' tacit knowledge, experience and intuition. In this paper, we present a study that investigated designers' textile sourcing activities and if and how digital tools could provide support. The study was conducted in a textile fair with an expert audience in the mind-set of sourcing. An existing digital tool that allows textiles manipulation was introduced to familiarise participants with the digital context and enable conversations on the future of textiles sourcing. We also look at the implications of adopting digital tools for their activities including a transition to more sustainable practices. The results raise awareness of designers' use of experiential information to support textiles sourcing, besides highlighting requirements for designing future digital tools.

KEYWORDS: *design research, design tools, textiles selection, tactile interactions, user experience.*

INTRODUCTION

Fashion has significant economic weight as an industry¹ and textile selection is crucial for its success. Textile selection involves aspects of function and subjective experience. Technical assessments for characterisation and performance are extensively supported by standards and machinery (Behery, 2005), providing the industry with rigorous specifications (Bang, 2009), whereas more subjective characteristics are heavily reliant on designers' tacit knowledge, experience and intuition.

¹ In 2009 overall industry contributions to United Kingdom economy were expected to achieve £20.9 billion (British Fashion Council, 2009).

This highlights a need to support the balance between technical and experiential information as noted in materials and design research (Ashby and Johnson, 2003; Miodownik, 2007; Karana et al., 2008, 2009; Van Kesteren, 2010; Rognoli, 2010; Karana et al., 2013). Further investigations are needed to expand the development of tools for textile sourcing to support designers' use of experiential information.

Previous research presented methods for objectively and subjectively assessing haptic properties of fabrics for quality assurance and predicting performance for engineering purposes (Behery, 2005). However, engineering-based research requires specialist knowledge for its use and interpretation, and the relation to intangible characteristics is not straightforward. Therefore, it has been of little or no use for designers

wishing to communicate formal and expressive features in a meaningful manner to stakeholders (Pedgley, 2009). More recently triads and design games to facilitate articulation of emotional values were proposed (Bang, 2011), but are still not widespread in industry.

Interactive technology developments to support design activities were noticed (e.g. Dillon et al., 2000; Magnenat-Thalmann and Bonanni, 2008; Philpott and Summers, 2012), but little research was conducted specifically to support textile sourcing. Here we present a study conducted at a textile trade fair to explore (1) how designers source textiles and engage with them during this process; and (2) if and how digital tools could support designers in this activity. We report the results and their implications on the design of tools to support textile sourcing. Before presenting our study, we review the related literature.

It is common practice in the fashion and textiles field to travel abroad visiting fairs where companies showcase their latest innovations. We chose this context for the investigation as it also offered an ecological approach as we could observe and question experts while they were performing the sourcing activity. As interactive digital tools for handling fabrics are at an embryonic stage and most textile experts may lack experience of using them, an App called iShoogle (Orzechowski, 2010) was presented as a research tool; its use aimed to cue textile experts to discuss how such tools should be designed for use in sourcing activities, as well as to identify in which stage(s) of the design process they would be desirable.

The fair we attended focuses on fabrics with reduced environmental impact. As such, we considered that the visiting experts would be open to the idea of digital tools that could offer new more sustainable alternatives to the current market models for sourcing textiles. We wanted to understand experts' perceptions of their current practice and how open they are to change to more sustainable conduct, provided that technology offers alternatives to gather the information they need about materials.

BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

In this section, a literature review is presented following our research questions. The first section comprises what is known about designer's sourcing of textiles, including research into the design process (focusing on useful information for materials selection) and textile-engineering research (highlighting the focus given to perceptions of textiles elicited through the sense of touch). The second section comprises analogue and digital tools to support designers when sourcing, with applications in research, industry and retail.

What is known about designers' sourcing of textiles?

Designers' knowledge

Fashion and textile designers are familiar with the physical characteristics and aesthetics of textiles, besides its suit-

able applications and contexts of use. They rely on multiple resources for inspiration and research—personal, cultural, market and trend related (Bang, 2009)—which they must skillfully articulate in design proposals and communicate to design teams and stakeholders, to guarantee their concepts are translated through manufacture and use. Such knowledge is innate (reliant on designers' sensibility and intuition) and tacit (acquired through training and experience) (Dormer, 1997).

Fashion and textile designers share similar design process patterns that usually move iteratively from a problem, question or need towards a solution (Design Council UK, 2005; Newman, 2011). Communication in this process is usually verbal, visual or through samples, and frequently multimodal. This recalls Dormer's (1997) definition of distributed knowledge that designers rely on the environment they work within—the social, organisation and the physical environment—to form their knowledge basis, test concepts and support decision-making processes. Fashion and textile designers use, for example, mood boards, samples and toiles as “things to think with” (Kirsh, 2013) and communicate or explicit their thoughts through. Kirsh (2013) suggests sensory experience and interaction with things as crucial for our understanding; which is also why prototypes facilitate reasoning, simulation and focusing by allowing people to project their ideas, creating “cognitive support”. This is aligned to the embodied cognition perspective, which proposes that we perceive the world with connected body and mind (Merleau-Ponty, 2002).

Touch for fabric sourcing

Studies show that clothing texture is a pervasive element to human perception (Laughlin, 1991), that tactile interaction is crucial for consumers primary judgments of product quality (Jordan, 2008) and that marketing communications incorporating tactile elements leads to increased emotional response in consumers that may influence decision-making processes (Peck and Wiggins, 2006). So far, textiles-related research mainly focused on verifying the effect of physical characteristics and performance of textiles, to support the description of attributes perceived through touch, and for predicting textiles' characteristics in manufacturing and quality control. Studies mostly covered themes of ‘fabric hand’, comfort to wear and aesthetic responses (Brandt et al., 1998). ‘Fabric hand’ is a disseminated concept in the textile industry. The definition we adopt (Atkinson et al., 2013) was proposed by Philippe et al. (2003) as “... the reaction of the sense of touch, when fabrics are held in the hand. (...) ‘hand’ can be considered as a meta-concept that takes into account not only the sensory aspect but also aspects such as formability, aesthetics, drapability and tailorability”. Most available definitions are included in a recent review on the hand of textiles (Ciesielska-Wróbel and Van Langenhove, 2012), which the authors combined to devise their own definition of the subjective hand of textiles.

Subjective analysis has been employed for characterisation of the tactile properties of textiles (Bensaid et al., 2006), to assess consumer preferences (Philippe et al., 2003), to verify

quality and suitability of new fibres, material structures and finishing, and for fibre blend characteristics of handle analysis (Howorth and Oliver, 1958). Diverse methods have been applied in subjectively assessing fabrics considering the many variables involved (Laughlin, 1991, Guest and Spence, 2003, Philippe et al., 2003, Behery, 2005). In pursuit of more tangible information, objective measurements serve to complement subjective analysis (Howorth and Oliver, 1958, Cho et al., 2002). In objective evaluation (Behery, 2005; Kawabata, 1982), the properties of a textile are assigned numerical values, which can then be interpreted to indicate how it is expected to feel (e.g. a fabric with a high bending rigidity measurement is expected to feel stiff). Objective systems require specialist technical knowledge to interpret results and this approach overlooks the semantics related or intangible information. Therefore, it has limited use for designers, whose selections are largely based on their sensibilities and experience acquired through training and practice (Bang, 2007).

Tools to support designers

Resources for sourcing

Physical materials libraries and trade fairs offer a wide range of materials and are curated to showcase the most innovative, allowing designers and product developers to be updated in terms of future trends (Mani et al., 2013). Besides the objective information related to characteristics and performance of materials, many factors must be considered for supporting the subjective experience, e.g. mode of display, environmental conditions, accessibility (Amaral et al., 2012). Digital databases offer predominantly technical information on a wide range of materials that can be retrieved, compared and connected to suppliers. Product engineers and material scientists are their main users to whom performance rather than aesthetic needs are paramount (Mani et al., 2013). Here the cognitive ergonomics is crucial to navigate the information system (textual and visual content), for the understanding and comparison of samples (Amaral et al., 2012).

More recently initiatives were noticed such as the Making app², a tool for comparing materials based on Nike's Materials Sustainability Index (MSI), which specifically provide designers with sustainability-related information.

Sensory and aesthetic approaches for selecting materials

Research into general materials selection explored subjective aspects to support designers beyond technical specifications requirements. These approaches are more experience-related and often subject to culture, market, time, place and context diversity. Such initiatives are user-centred and reveal novel approaches to include stakeholders in the design process, i.e. material selection. Some included the development of tools, such as the Meanings of Materials tool (Karana, 2009), which guides participants on the investigation of

2 Further information available at Nike Makers website. Information retrieved in July 29, 2014 from <http://nikemakers.com>

sensory aspects of materials that they relate to a predefined design intention; the Expressive-Sensorial Atlas of materials (Rognoli, 2010), which links objective properties to subjective qualities through the use of illustrative charts; and the Stakeholder Game (Bang, 2011), which engage stakeholders in a game to develop emotional concepts for future design based on personal experience. There is also an automotive industry tool created by Renault, the Sensotact®, a reference instrument for the tactile characterisation of materials (Al-lione et al., 2012).

Interactive tools supporting design

Besides research-oriented or materials selection tools, the industry provides practical tools, which support designers' activities and are accessible even to non-experts. These tools mediate designers' interactions with materials (organising and/or augmenting their sensory perception or providing 'invisible' technical information) and support the design process at different stages.

Some examples are the Pantone paper tools and Capsure,³ which facilitate communication by providing a common language to guarantee colour definition and reproduction; and Adobe Kuler⁴, a synthesis of colour research into a tool for both experts and non-experts. This could be extended to interact with other senses as in the Ophone⁵, a sensory communication tool that allows sending olfactory messages instantly over long distances, or through haptic feedback as presented in the Poke project (Park et al., 2013).

Interactive technologies for e-retail, or fashion and textiles co-design are emerging to support designers' activities. Whilst interesting progress is being made in overcoming technological limitations, these show and adopt a narrow understanding of experiencing fabrics, as they do not support natural engagement of the senses (e.g. touch, sound). Developments initially focused on visual and verbal channels, and only recently studies are addressing tactile aspects (Dillon et al., 2000; Magnenat-Thalmann and Bonanni, 2008; Wu et al., 2011; Philpott and Summers, 2012), mostly through tactile feedback. Still, current interactive media presentations of textiles poorly communicate their 'hand' and less attention was given to gestures for handling textiles, or other properties (e.g. sound) and therefore to the type of technology needed to support such experiences.

Atkinson et al. (2013) addressed the latter question, showing that textiles are animated differently in response to being handled with different gestures. Gestures used by non-experts to assess textiles through hand tactile interaction were explored, and from these observations techniques were devised to create interactive simulations of digital textile han-

3 Retrieved in January 21, 2014 from <http://www.pantone.co.uk/pages/products/product.aspx?pid=1433&ca=7>

4 Retrieved in January 21, 2014 from <http://www.adobe.com/products/kuler.html>

5 Retrieved in January 21, 2014 from <http://lelaboratoire.org/CP%20Olfactive%20Project%20ENG%2013.04.09.pdf>

dling for touch-based display (Atkinson et al., 2013). The experiments highlighted that the use of gesture influences the level of user engagement, possibly due to visual and proprioceptive feedback (Bianchi-Berthouze, 2013; Wu et al., 2011), and emphasised restrictions presented by the flat, rigid displays to the users' experience as they limit and alter the types of gestures that can be used to handle textiles. Building on this knowledge, we took an embodiment perspective of affective touch behaviour in experiencing textiles (Petreca et al., 2013), to discuss how an experiential perspective may be more aligned with designers' activities.

FUTURE FABRICS EXPO (FFE) STUDY

We proposed a qualitative explorative study with specialists in the fashion and textiles field to investigate their sourcing activities. We used an existing interactive tool, iShoogle (Orzechowski, 2010), to familiarise participants with the digital context and enable the investigation of their behaviour and to verify opportunities for developing digital tools to support textiles sourcing.

Method

Context of study

The study was conducted in-situ during the third FFE (organised by the Sustainable Angle⁶) held at Fashion SVP⁷ in London on 22-24 September 2013. The fair exhibits hundreds of textiles from more than 50 international companies committed to reducing environmental impact throughout the supply chain. In this fair, as in many others, visitors are not allowed to collect samples immediately but rather request them from exhibitors.

Design of the study

The study explored fashion designers' behaviour and needs when selecting textiles, around the questions: How designers source textiles? and how digital tools could support designers in this activity? These were addressed through the following activities:

1. Investigating designers' needs: Participants responded to an introductory questionnaire providing information related to their field of expertise and textile sourcing activities, concerning criteria for selecting and knowledge base. Considering time constraints inherent in the fair, questions were simplified in a manner that would still

Figure 1. Picture from the study setup. © The Sustainable Angle Photography Green Lens Studios 2013. Source: <http://www.thesustainableangle.org/futurefabricsexpo/Photos/FutureFabricsExpo2013.aspx>

provide necessary insight into their information needs.

2. Investigating designers' reactions to a digital tool: Participants interacted with digital samples to express their impressions of them and discuss opportunities for digital tools, prompted by open-ended questions displayed on a board to which their answers were attached using sticky notes (Figure 1). The questions were related, but not limited to the tool being demonstrated.

Participants

The study was approved by the Local Ethics Committee and participants provided written consent. Participants were recruited at the fair and had been identified beforehand as a specialist audience. In total, 24 visitors participated in the study, half of which had more than three years of professional experience, and the other half, up to three years of experience or were still completing undergraduate courses. Their specialty was distributed between apparel industry (12 participants), education (4 participants) and others (8 participants).

Apparatus

The main apparatus were an introductory questionnaire for activity one and the iShoogle tool and board with questions for activity two.

1. Introductory questionnaire
The questionnaire had four questions: two concerning designers' area of specialty to certify they were specialists in the field; the third question involved criteria for selecting fabrics and the fourth included sources of information designers' use when selecting textiles. Multiple-choice options were developed for questions 3 and 4 with reference to the literature, in Tables 1 and 2, where only the first column was presented in the questionnaire. Answers were chosen from a provided answer sheet.
2. Using 'iShoogle' to explore the scope for digital tools to support designers when sourcing fabrics

6 The Sustainable Angle are a not for profit organisation which supports fashion companies to make informed decisions around sustainability. Information retrieved in January 21, 2014, from <http://www.thesustainableangle.org/>

7 This is a fashion-sourcing event in the United Kingdom for buying directly from manufacturers. Information retrieved in January 21, 2014 from <http://www.fashionsvp.com>

OPTION	DEFINITION	TERM MENTIONED BY	CATEGORY
Application	Aspects related to the context of use	Jenkins and Lamb, 1987	Objective
Composition	Quantified fibre type	Jenkins and Lamb, 1987	
Fibre characteristics	The physical properties that differentiate fibres. Fibres can be natural (vegetable or animal) or man-made (synthetic and artificial). They differ in terms of performance, comfort, durability, care and price, amongst other specific qualities	Jenkins and Lamb, 1987	
Performance	Related to the material behaviour under specific conditions and in use	Van Kersteren, 2008	
Thermal properties	Physical properties related to touch perception: thermal capacity and thermal conductivity	Karana et al, 2008; Rognoli, 2010	
Cost	One of the main constraints when sourcing materials	Ashby and Johnson, 2010; Karana et al, 2008	
Intuition	Designer subjectivity influences the decision	Karana et al, 2010	Subjective
Enjoyment	Appeal to the senses	Lee et al., 2010	
Intention	Intended meaning of the product, expressed through intangible aspects	Ashby and Johnson, 2010; Karana et al, 2010	
Sensory stimulation	Subjective sensations evoked by manipulating the material	Rognoli, 2010; Van Kersteren, 2008	
Aesthetic	Related to how the materials appeal the senses	Ashby and Johnson, 2010; Karana et al, 2008; Van Kersteren, 2008	
Pleasurable touch	Appeal to the sense of touch	Karana et al, 2010	Objective and/or subjective
Properties of texture	Properties perceived in interaction with textiles (subjective), which are objectively measurable and can be achieved through different compositions, constructions and finishes. Important for comfort	Jenkins and Lamb, 1987	
Design brief	Defined objectives and constraints for the product	Karana et al, 2010	
Other	Left blank for participants' input	-	-

Table 1. Questionnaire options for criteria for selecting fabrics (Question 3) further categorised into objective and subjective

OPTION	DEFINITION	TERM MENTIONED BY
Exhibitions	Art and design related exhibitions. Form part of designers' experience	Van Kersteren, 2008
Personal experience	Knowledge from education and previous projects	Van Kersteren, 2008
Supplier or manufacturer	Provide information through direct consultation	Van Kersteren, 2008; Karana et al, 2008
Sample collections	From previous projects or commercial collections	Van Kersteren, 2008
Internet	Use of the internet to search for materials and suppliers	Van Kersteren, 2008; Karana et al, 2008

Tradeshows	Information about latest materials and solutions	Van Kersteren, 2008
Books	Used as source of general information about materials	Van Kersteren, 2008; Karana et al, 2008
Tests and experiments	Experimenting with materials or tested by specialised third parties	Van Kersteren, 2008
Example products	Previously bought or seen in advertisement; from competitors	Van Kersteren, 2008
Magazines	Trend or suppliers information	Van Kersteren, 2008; Karana et al, 2008
Brochures	Brochures are sent from materials suppliers	Van Kersteren, 2008; Karana et al, 2008
Personal collection	Samples stored from previous projects, findings from shops or trips.	Van Kersteren, 2008
Databases	Software tools that support general selection	Van Kersteren, 2008
Films	Form part of designers experience and repertoire	*
Vintage shops; Museums	Considering fashion cyclic trends, museums and vintage shops can serve as research for identifying materials of interest. They also form designers' experience.	*
Apps	Provide designers with information about materials (e.g. Materials Council and Making app)	*

Table 2. Questionnaire options for information sources (Question 4)

* Items added considering current industry developments and practices specific to fashion designers, which were not included in other literature.

'iShoogle' was used as a boundary object (Lee, 2007) to explore the potential of digital tools support for selecting fabrics. iShoogle consists of an application that enables people to manipulate fabrics through different gestures and is meant to convey fabric behaviour. FFE organisers selected four fabrics from the fair and digital samples were created from them, following the methodology described by Atkinson et al. (2013). The fabrics—heavy jersey (Figure 2a), linen jersey (Figure 2b), denim (Figure 2c) and felt (Figure 2d)—were showcased on first and second-generation iPads at the fair. Because of the diverse characteristics of these fabrics, they differed especially in movement behaviour. Figure 3 shows the iShoogle gesture interactions for manipulation of the digital fabric samples.

We explored three main themes through six questions (Table 3); the latter were displayed on a board and after engaging with the digital interactive videos of the fabrics, participants wrote down answers on sticky notes and attached them to the board. Each theme was given a broader focus, considering the overall aim of the study was to get a comprehensive understanding and scope the opportunities for digital tools developments. The theme regarding touch behaviour when interacting with fabrics has been investigated in greater depth in previous studies (Atkinson et al., 2013), focusing on consumers. Therefore, in this study we chose a design (expert) community for comparison.

Figure 2. Fabrics used to create digital samples

Figure 3. Gestural interactions with digital samples through iShoogle
 3a. Horizontal stroke, 3b. Vertical stroke, 3c. Horizontal pinch, 3d. Vertical pinch, 3e. Scrunch

ANALYSIS

All data was transcribed for analysis using the Thematic Analysis method, following Braun and Clarke’s (2006) guidelines. Coding was conducted using QSR International’s NVivo 10 software. The questions were used to guide the analysis, but focus was given to themes and sub-themes that emerged from responses, which are described in the results section.

Results

The results from activities 1 and 2 are reported separately in the following subsections.

Sourcing criteria and information needs

Participants’ responses to criteria for selecting fabrics (Table 4) are balanced between objective (functional) and subjective (experiential) characteristics of textiles. Other aspects such as cost and environmental issues are important, as indicated in previous research (Ashby and Johnson, 2010; Van Kersteren, 2008; Karana et al, 2008). Therefore, designers’ criteria when selecting materials previously identified in design research could be extrapolated for the fashion and textiles arena; however, this should be evaluated by further research to verify the impact of trends and culture on fashion designers’ decisions for textiles.

Answers were distributed between criteria (Table 4) and remained inconclusive (the highest agreement was found with 8 out of 21 respondents), meriting further investigation. The least chosen options were ‘Intuition’ and ‘Enjoyment’, which are subjective and in contrast to the most selected option ‘Composition’. This early evidence seems to indicate that designers perceive their selection as more related to objective criteria. However, three (‘Properties of texture’, ‘Aesthetic’ and ‘Fibre characteristics’) out of the five most frequent criteria are characteristics of fabrics that are experienced through the senses. Also, ‘Properties of texture’ are largely experienced through touch, although they can be objectively measured. When clustering criteria only as objective and subjective (categorisation in Table 1), further differences are noticed, with ‘objective criteria’ being selected 31 times,

NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS	CRITERIA CHOSEN
8	Composition
6	Properties of texture
6	Aesthetic
6	Fibre characteristics
5	Application
5	Cost
5	Intention
5	Pleasurable touch
4	Other - sustainability
3	Design brief
3	Performance
3	Sensory stimulation
1	Intuition
3	No answer was provided

Table 4. Key criteria used for selecting fabrics (participants selected 3 options, 4 participants didn’t reply)

NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS	FREQUENCY OF CHOICE		
	Objective criteria	Subjective criteria	Objective and/or subjective criteria
5	1	1	1
5	1	2	0
3	2	1	0
3	2	0	1
3*	0	0	0
2	3	0	0
1	0	2	1
1	2	0	0
1	1	0	0

Table 5. Distribution of criteria used for selecting fabrics (clustered categories of objective and subjective criteria)

* No answer was provided

NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS	INFORMATION SOURCE
17	Exhibitions
13	Personal experience
13	Supplier or manufacturer
12	Sample collections
12	Internet
12	Tradeshows
10	Books
8	Museums
8	Tests and experiments
7	Example products
7	Magazines
6	Vintage shops
6	Brochures
5	Films
4	Personal collection
4	Databases
3	Apps

Table 6. Information sources used by designers when selecting fabrics (participants selected as many options as they judged applicable)

‘subjective criteria’ selected 20 times and ‘objective and subjective’ selected 9 times. While verifying inter-personal differences to distribution criteria (Table 5), considering the clustered categories, it seems that most designers include a mix of objective and subjective criteria.

The sources used for informing fabric selection (Table 6) are varied and extend beyond technical specifications and objective information into designers’ personal experience, cultural and market influences, reiterating findings from the literature (Van Kersteren, 2008; Bang, 2009) and relating to the concept of distributed knowledge. Most participants selected several options as information sources, which remains too general in terms of their information needs and the amount of information absorbed. Designers use a mixture of sources (Table 6) and responses show the importance of experience for sourcing – there is higher use of more experiential material (e.g. Sample collections, Example products), immersive and socially engaging environments (e.g. Exhibitions, Tradeshows, Vintage Shops) than reference material and data only (e.g. Internet, Books, Brochures and Databases).

Exploration of existing digital tool: opportunities and needs

The results obtained from the iShoogle experiment indicated four main themes: touch for fabric sourcing, when and how tools can be integrated to the process of fabric sourcing, designers’ needs, and limitations and opportunities for digital tools development. These are described using the notation P# to indicate participants’ anecdotal evidence.

Figure 4. Designers’ touch behaviour for exploring textiles.

Touch for fabric sourcing

Results show that the gestures designers used (Figure 4) partially overlap with those observed in consumers (Atkinson et al. 2013) but also includes some new gestures. Whilst the most frequent gestures (rub, stroke, pinch and scrunch) were observed also in non-experts consumers (Atkinson et al. 2013), fold, pull and drape seem to be more specialist gestures, which were only noticed in the study with designers herein reported.

- *Movement and feel*

Participants considered that interactive videos provide a better idea of the fabric behaviour. “Gives a sense of drape qualities” (P22). They consider that digital samples could inform them about the movement and texture of fabrics, but still consider the manipulation of the actual fabric crucial for its appreciation. “To review texture and movement, yes. But it’s very important to touch for hand-feel” (P6).

Although participants provided brief answers, their understanding of ‘feel’ seems more related to sensory stimuli beyond their hand movement. This relates back to the definition by Philippe et al. (2003), which comprises both aspects. Overall, designers consider touching the textile a crucial step for their sourcing and believe that “The actual sampling will never go away completely” (P11).

When and how tools can be integrated to fabric sourcing process

- *Initial filter or research tool*

Participants consider interactive videos useful as a filter before traveling to textile fairs, declaring it a “Good starting point” (P6), but they still need to touch for making final decisions. They mentioned a tool would be useful for the initial stage of design, during the research process when they have to come up with ideas of textiles, before checking what suppliers’ have to offer.

“For the research it would be really useful, at the start of the creative process” (P5).

“You could filter samples down to your favourites” (P14).

Additionally, they consider that interactive tools could provide more information about fabrics’ behaviour, which they are not familiar with. Participants suggested that it would be interesting to produce a set of reference fabrics with interactive videos to be used as sourcing tool, in which different classes of fabrics would be represented through a condensed archive. Thus, indicating opportunities for development of supporting tools for research and ideation stages.

- Saving - time, space, money and travelling
Participants envisaged digital tools could be “Time saving” (P6), space saving [“... would be an interesting thing to replace big suitcase with an iPad” (P3)], facilitate “Quicker development process. Also possibly money saving” (P19), besides considering it a more resilient format than the current textile samples provided by industries [“Definitely save time! (...) Efficient and durable” (P24)], and still providing an experience through interaction [“Good to carry fabrics with you in a lighter and interactive way” (P23)].

In relation to reducing travel to fairs, positive and negative responses were balanced. Those who would minimise traveling are based on the premise that digital tools would facilitate their sourcing activities [“Yes, sure. If it was more effective, I wouldn’t travel” (P2)], but have reservations in relation to compromising the social side of fairs, where they have the chance to meet suppliers, colleagues and build networks. Some designers mentioned they “Would definitely still attend larger fairs” (P19). Also, the need for samples to be provided remains (P4, P7).

Those who would still travel would welcome the inclusion of digital means to support their current activities. “I source from hundreds of mills based on conversations. So no, but it might streamline the trip and help plan” (P8). “I find it important to meet people in the fair (producers), so I would like to see a combination of fair, but also being able to source online” (P10).

Designers’ needs

Besides the “need to feel the fabrics, as it is a very important decision” (P21) and to socialise at fairs, participants reported other needs, related to memory and communication within their projects. This can be in communication with suppliers [“Just talk to a supplier that responds to your needs. Useful” (P11)], through personal and others’ previous experience that inform their selection process [“Feedback from other companies help, or previous experience. But if the contact is new, you need more samples” (P4)], or making available “more images of fabric in use (as garment or draped)” (P19).

Furthermore, observations of designers’ behaviour highlighted that it is common practice to take pictures of exhibited fabrics, also registering their technical specifications (Figure 5)

Figure 5. Visitors taking photos and making annotations. © The Sustainable Angle Photography Green Lens Studios 2013. Source: <http://www.thesustainableangle.org/futurefabricsexpo/Photos/FutureFabricsExpo2013.aspx>

as samples generally cannot be taken and must be requested from suppliers by post. These factors indicate an opportunity for tools that support managing samples collected in fairs.

Digital tools development

- Limitations of the technology
Designers see interactive videos as a step ahead from the current online stills [“Gives more information than photos. Seems to be a good way to go... But how to give the textural information?” (P1)]. They would like to have more three-dimensional information and possibly related to a context of use. “It’s only shown flat. You can’t get the feeling from drape” (P23).
They consider that interactive videos would be useful “especially for online e-retailers” (P22), but still lack refinement for designers. Still, this demonstrates an opportunity for tools that support sourcing over distance providing an improvement on current experience.
- Opportunities for improvement
Some participants clearly expressed their expectations from a tool such as iShoogle (Orzechowski, 2010) mostly relating to improvements to “see fabric in different situations and in different manipulations” (P14). They also suggested additional features, such as magnifying and improving interactivity (P16) to support understanding of fabrics’ properties and agency (Repp and Knoblich, 2007). “Magnify / zoom. Stay once deformed. Connection between length of gesture and recovery” (P17), or showing different aspects “Combine verbal and visual descriptions. Show close ups and on a person” (P13).

DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

This study was motivated by our research questions on (1) how designers source textiles and engage with them during this process, and (2) if and how digital tools could support

designers in this activity. We reinforce that both the participants' sample size and the sustainability context of FFE are limitations to this study and could have biased responses. Results of the study are herein summarised and should feed into inspiration and requirements for digital tools:

- Designers consider touch imperative for experiencing textiles.
- Designers consider that a tool could make their sourcing process more efficient - time, space and moneywise.
- Designers believe a tool would be an addition to the selection process, but still need to see and feel fabric samples, interact and communicate with their stakeholders, and to share information about previous experience with suppliers and materials.
- Most participants selected a number of options as information sources. Research shows that different information sources are used at different stages of the design process (Van Kesteren, 2008; Karana et al, 2008), but we are still left with questions about how they organise, store and share this information, since their reports suggest that their own and others previous experiences are an important input for sourcing textiles.

Opportunities for development of digital tools

Research and ideation

Designers are interested in interactive video or broadly on digital tools that would support research, particularly in the early stages of material selection. If video-based, the tool ideally should convey three-dimensional and textural information, offer magnification and include a wider variety of manipulations, besides providing the basic technical specifications.

Sourcing over distance

Current tools and technology do not support articulation of designers' perceptions or remote communication of textiles properties. In terms of the impact digital tools could have in their practice, designers see potential benefits in adding efficiency and better informing decisions, but still do not fully embrace the idea of minimising travelling to fairs, due to their social dimension. From this small study, it is inconclusive whether digital textile sourcing would help to reduce environmental impact related to travels and textile waste generated by physical sampling, though it may give designers the opportunity to make more informed decisions.

Sample management

The study indicates opportunities for technology development and reinforces the importance of using physical textile samples as 'thinking tools' in design (Kirsh, 2013), once they play a key role, as identified by most participants. As samples are unavailable immediately and designers would take

pictures of the fabric and/or of the technical specifications, would it be helpful to have a way of producing a multimodal register that designers could take with them straight away?

Opportunities for alternative more experiential tools development

From the summary of results, it is clear that designers want and need to better understand and communicate about sensory properties of textiles; this is an integral part of choosing textiles, and touching is the one single thing that no participant would remove from their fabric sourcing process. Sensory perception facilitates cognition; this is reinforced by designers' need to feel the fabric as a crucial step for understanding and making decisions. This is aligned to the distributed knowledge and embodied cognition perspectives, and is also complemented by the view of Tallis (2003) that from tactile interaction people develop "tactile knowledge", which "...is acquired serially (...) a cumulative understanding of the properties of individual objects". Participants' responses indicate that when experiencing a textile, one gets an understanding of it and of how it feels. The fair environment seems to be an "enactive landscape" where designers act "in a goal-oriented manner" (Kirsh, 2013), experiencing fabrics for selecting those suitable for their designs. Moreover, designers argue that the social side of fairs is important for sourcing, which from a distributed knowledge perspective potentially indicates that designers' decisions are more a team activity (design team and stakeholders) than individual. The results obtained from this study will inform the creation of new concept tools that will be tested at a future fair.

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“RHETORICAL ABILITY”: REASON, EMOTION, AND CHARACTER AS HEURISTICS FOR THE EVALUATION OF EFFICACY IN DESIGN

G. Mauricio Mejía
University of Caldas, Colombia
✉ mauricio.mejiaramirez@ucaldas.edu.co

Sauman Chu
University of Minnesota, USA
✉ schu@umn.edu

ABSTRACT

Usability inspection is a major standard for design evaluation in which expert evaluators use heuristics to assess efficiency and quality. However, usability alone is insufficient to assess efficacy in design problems in which the main design goal is not cognitive interaction. For example, goals such as social change (e.g. health promotion), communication, or entertainment, in the field of product and system design, require design evaluation that goes beyond usability. In this paper we argue that rhetorical ability (or *rhetorability*) is a plausible heuristic evaluation approach in the field of design for social change. We propose nine heuristics based on the three rhetorical appeals, logos (reason), pathos (emotion), and ethos (credibility). The applicability of the method depends on the understanding of the rhetorical situation; thus, the rhetorical ability heuristic evaluator should be an expert in the audience needs, the design goal, and the design problem.

KEYWORDS: *design evaluation, expert evaluation, rhetorical ability, rhetorical appeals, design efficacy, design for social change.*

INTRODUCTION

The expert evaluation of a design outcome (image, product, service, or system) may be carried out from different perspectives depending on the evaluation goal. One perspective is ease or efficiency of use; another is efficacy of the goal. Usability inspection is a type of expert evaluation for finding usability problems in interactive products (Nielsen, 1994). It focuses on efficiency and has become a major standard for several reasons. First, the introduction of digital interactive systems with complex human-machine interactions generated a need for evaluation methods and design principles capable of helping designers reduce cognitive friction for users (see Cooper, Reiman, & Cronin, 2007). Second, experts are able to carry out a rapid assessment with relatively simple observations. Further, usability can be used as a tool to indirectly argue other benefits such as visits and usage.

Another perspective is efficacy in terms of the design goal. To directly assess efficacy in design goals such as increased sales, political persuasion, or social change, usability can provide insights into people's ability to employed or interact with the design outcome. However, it is insufficient to assess goal efficacy. General expert evaluation methods can be used to assess efficacy in design, but there are no heuristics to

guide the assessment process. We propose using heuristics based on the theory of rhetoric to assess the efficacy of design outcomes, with a focus on design for social change. We call this heuristics rhetorical ability or *rhetorability*.

THEORY OF RHETORIC FOR DESIGN EVALUATION

Aristotle wrote his *Rhetoric* more than two thousand years ago. By his time, rhetoric was understood as a persuasive art for public speaking in political debate, courts and public events in a context of Greece's emerging democracy. Today, rhetorical theory has been used in different fields to study varied social phenomena. Buchanan has reviewed rhetoric with a view to theorizing the design field, arguing that rhetoric was one of the first design activities (Buchanan, 1995). According to Schriver (1997), the preoccupation with the audience and context in the Russian constructivist or German Bauhaus design movements initiated the rhetorical approach to design.

In practical terms relevant to the field of design, rhetoric is a method that serves both for the analysis and production of design outcomes (Bonsiepe, 2000; Buchanan, 1985). Since rhetoric can be used for analysis, it also has a particular

potential to be used in evaluation. In the modern theory of rhetoric in design, it has been proposed that the diverse rhetorical components might be used to understand the design activity. For example, in classic rhetoric there are five canons or divisions for the speech creation process: invention (finding arguments), arrangement or disposition (ordering arguments), style (form of expression), memory, and delivery or action. These canons are a model that can be used to define five phases for design production (Ehse, 1984) or to organize designers' abilities and their correspondence to design specialties (Buchanan, 1995).

The component of rhetoric that is best suited to analyze and assess the characteristics of design outcomes is rhetorical appeals (Mejía & Chu, 2014). According to Aristotle rhetorical appeals or modes of persuasion are: the truth or apparent truth of the arguments (logos), leading the audience to feel emotions (pathos), and the credibility of the spoken word (ethos) (Aristotle & Kennedy, 1991). In simple terms, logos refers to appeals to reason, pathos appeals to emotion, and ethos appeals to credibility. As is the case for any speech, design consists of a persuasive argument that has recourse to the three appeals. The division between them is an artificial theoretical concept for analysis.

Aristotle explained that when there are not enough facts or evidence, rhetorical production can help make decisions (Aristotle & Kennedy, 1991). Alternatively, when the facts and evidence are insufficient to change social behaviors, rhetorical appeals can arguably constitute a powerful tool. For example, there is strong evidence to suggest that poor diets and lack of exercise cause obesity, but merely communicating this evidence is not enough to change health behaviors. Removing premises in order to generate logos appeals or incorporating pathos and ethos indices may be more effective in bringing about change. Furthermore, the challenge is greater with low-skilled low-literacy audiences. The rhetorician-designer seeks to create effective speech-designs that aid social change, using rhetorical appeals rather than evidence to help people take action in the desired direction.

Braet (1992) provided a useful reflection regarding the argumentative nature of the three rhetorical appeals. He reviewed them in Aristotle's work, seeking to assess if pathos and ethos could be considered enthymemes (arguments). He first demonstrated that the logos appeal is the central enthymeme of a speech. He then explained that the pathos and ethos appeals could have two uses: one as indices shown (interpreted by the audience) and one as arguments proven (presented by the speaker). He explained that using pathos or ethos as enthymemes may counter the persuasion goal. For example, "attempting to prove ethos would produce doubt about the ethos! Only when one is certain that the ethos has been undermined by prejudices, can proving the ethos make sense" (p. 312). Also, enthymematic pathos could reduce the strength of the emotion, or be useless. Braet concluded that in an effective speech, logos enthymeme or argument might be combined with ethos and/or pathos indices. Adapting Braet's interpretation to the field of design means that logos

is the base appeal in design outcomes, to which pathos and ethos indices may be added to a greater or lesser degree.

DESIGN RESEARCH ON RHETORICAL APPEALS

Rhetorical appeals have been used distinctively as tools for analysis of design outcomes and as research variables. In a theoretical essay, Buchanan (1985), analyzed the rhetorical appeals of industrial design products like spoons, coffee mills, and lamps in a discussion about the need to create more intelligible products and to enhance the ways in which designers communicate with their audiences. He argued that logos refers to how designers propose a technological reasoning and practical functions for objects, how pathos refers to the ways in which designers put users in emotional states to generate desire and satisfaction, and how ethos refers to the ways they gain credibility by showing concern for the audience and creating confidence about the use of objects.

A different application of rhetoric in design is the practical framework for graphic design production developed by Ehse (2008). He described the application of concepts of rhetoric such as rhetorical situation and rhetorical canons, but placed particular emphasis on rhetorical appeals and rhetorical figures. He argued that there are logos-driven graphic design products such as wayfinding design or instructional documents, pathos-driven products such as advertisements and ethos-driven products such as social and health topics. He also operationalized rhetorical appeals strategies; for logos: the organization of information, choice of fonts, hierarchy, and consistency with the goal of facilitating understanding; for pathos: special arrangements, visual symbolism, and choice of images and colors with the goal of triggering emotions; while for ethos the strategy is a simple translation from rhetoric: employing a general conceptual approach in order to provide credibility, empathy, and reliability. These strategies are limited to visual composition elements. Van der Waarde (2010) used Ehse's rhetorical framework as a reference for an analysis of communication in European medical pamphlets, discussing the rhetorical situation, canons, and appeals. He argued that the components of rhetoric served as tools to explain failures in communication standards.

Recently, one of the authors of this paper was involved in two studies, one of which used rhetorical appeals to conduct an analysis of viral videos for social change (Mejía & Longo, 2012). The authors interviewed experts and analyzed the rhetorical appeals in four videos including *The Story of Stuff* (The Story of Stuff Project, 2007) - an animation presented by Annie Leonard about the negative environmental effects of the production and consumption of industrial goods and *RSA Animate - The Crisis of Capitalism* (Royal Society for the Encouragement of Arts, Manufactures, and Commerce, RSA, 2010) - a lecture by David Harvey animated with real-time drawings that explains the oppressive effects of capitalism and claims the need for action. They identified salient indices of appeals

to logos, pathos, and ethos. After publication these salient indices were reviewed and refined:

Logos

- Simplicity (of content and use of redundant visual elements)
- Simple rational metaphors (using color or shape)
- Audio-visual consistency (or synchrony between audio and visual information)
- Appropriate symbols (for the audience)
- Rational narrative style (such as documentary or lecture)
- Use of evidence (such as facts or historical information)
- Directions of action (to be taken for social change)

Pathos

- Emotional elements (that are playful, positive, or aggressive such as humor, hope, or danger)
- Ethical content (such as claims of corruption, irresponsibility or greed to elicit emotional reactions)
- Reception comfort (such as a sense of calm or urgency generated in the audience)
- Audience sensitive content (such as disturbing content)

Ethos

- Neutrality (information appears to be objective or biased)
- Visual style is empathetic (with the experiences of the audience)
- Narrator appearance (in coherence with the message)
- Narrator profile (in coherence with the message)
- Narrator tone (in coherence with the message)
- Supporting organization (increases reputation of the message)

In the second study, Mejía explored and evaluated rhetorical appeal strategies used in design for social change; specifically an interactive product for obesity prevention targeted at Latinos (Mejía, 2013). The study explored rhetorical appeals, designing a mobile web application with three versions, or modes, each using different rhetorical appeal strategies. The infographic mode focused on logos and had a reduced number of pathos and ethos indices, the comic mode had increased pathos indices and the realistic mode had increased ethos indices. The data was collected using auto-observation during the design process, which was examined by design experts using rhetorical appeal heuristics and through qualitative interviews in a real world context. The author, the external design experts and the audience had different perceptions regarding the rhetorical appeals. In the design process, the author had initially planned different rhetorical strategies but in the end concluded that they were similar. The design experts found significant differences, while the users interviewed did not perceive any. The study concluded that de-

signers lend their attention to visual and textual elements and overlook the influence of the design concept, format, and interactivity on the rhetorical appeals.

Building on this existing research, the following section of this paper presents the proposed rhetorical ability heuristics. Admittedly, grounded evidence directly related to the design of rhetorical appeals is limited; nonetheless, rhetorical theory shows great promise both for the production and the evaluation of persuasive design intended to change people's behaviors.

RHETORICAL ABILITY HEURISTICS

This section discusses concepts of rhetorical appeal and proposes heuristics for evaluating design using the findings of research into rhetorical appeals found in the design research literature.

Logos – reason

Aristotle explained that logos is the logical argument presented either in the form of enthymemes or paradigms. Enthymemes are incomplete syllogisms in which a reason is provided alongside a conclusion (Aristotle & Kennedy, 1991). For example the syllogism “he is healthy because he eats vegetables” is an enthymeme; the complete syllogism would be “People who eat vegetables are healthy. He eats vegetables. Therefore, he is healthy”. Paradigms are inductions that consist of stating a particular observation and leaving the conclusion unstated (Aristotle & Kennedy). For example, “he became healthier eating more vegetables” is a paradigm. Design strategies or characteristics are difficult to identify as enthymemes or paradigms unless there is explicit verbal content that takes those forms. Consequently, rational elements or strategies that induce rational/logical thinking or facilitate cognitive processing are identified as appeals to logos. Points 1. to 3., below, describe the rhetorical ability heuristics we propose that are associated with appeals to reason:

1. *Perceptual information and interactive structure facilitate cognitive processing.*

At the level of visual composition, this heuristic encompasses Ehses' (2008) logos strategies to facilitate understanding (organization of information, choice of fonts, hierarchy, and consistency). Depending on the media employed, interactive structures such as audio-visual consistency in videos (Mejía & Longo, 2012) may become relevant. This heuristic is related to general usability heuristics proposed by Nielsen (Nielsen, 1995). However, rational persuasion is not the same as usable and human-centered design. The design must strategically provide information and interaction to help people change their knowledge, attitudes, or behaviors. The perceptual information and interactive structures are adequate in quantity and level of complexity according to the rhetorical situation. While some situations may require large amounts

of information and high complexity in information and interaction (e.g. asking medical doctors to change medical procedures), other situations may require limited information and low complexity (e.g. asking poor people to increase their savings). In general, the information presented and the interaction options should help people to reason. This demands that the designer should decide about the adequate “dosage”, or quantity, of information and the complexity of the experience. In social change goals, presenting limited information might help to nudge people towards adopting desired behaviors.

2. *Level of abstraction matches the audience's skills and culture*

High abstraction that is adequate for high-skill high-literacy people is not always the best design solution. Generally, for low-skill low-literacy audiences or people from a particular culture, low abstraction (or high iconicity) would help to understand directions or messages. Krampen (1965) suggested that graphic symbols could be used in developing countries to help communicate information among audiences with low literacy. He argued that, for these countries, design should consist of simple and realistic graphic symbols because the use of style or attractive expression may confuse the audience. Also, Latino parents in an underserved community showed preference for realistic illustrations of children over infographic-like abstractions to represent levels of obesity in a logical way (Mejía, 2013). Furthermore, people from specific cultures may not understand some very abstracted symbols that are designed for ideal universal audiences, such as AIGA symbols for men's and women's restrooms. The exception to this rule is the use of cultural symbols that are highly abstracted yet easy to understand because people are familiar with them.

3. *Logical explanations are provided, preferably within the duration of the interaction routine.*

In the audiovisual medium this could be controlled, because all information is processed during the interaction. The salient indices of rational narrative style and use of evidence in viral videos developed by Mejía and Longo (2012) illustrate this. However, in other design outcomes such as interactive websites, industrial products, or services, logical explanations are not provided in the interaction routine. A classic problem in industrial products is people trying to use products without reading the accompanying manuals, either because they are not willing to make the effort or because the manual is for some reason not at hand. Van der Waarde (2010) described another example, explaining that information in medical pamphlets follows a logical order required by the relevant European Directive. He argued that the overwhelming list of side effects compared to the short description of benefits hinders patients' ability to make rational decisions. Additionally, whereas the likelihood of side effects is provided, the probability of effectiveness is not. This is an example of a lack of logical explanation and an exaggerated exten-

sion of explanation for the interaction routine, which illustrates a cause of failure to persuade people to take their medicines.

Pathos – emotion

Aristotle explained that leading the audience to feel certain emotions of pleasure or pain is an appeal to pathos. These emotions are temporary states of mind and affect audience judgment. According to Aristotle the emotions pathos opposes are anger/calmness, friendliness/hostility, fear/confidence, shame/shamelessness, kindness/unkindness, pity/indignation, and envy/emulation. The positive or negative emotion is used depending on the rhetorical situation (Aristotle & Kennedy, 1991). Pathos heuristics consist of applying Aristotle's description directly: does the design outcome lead the audience to feel the adequate emotions? Points 4. to 6., below, constitute a list of the proposed rhetorical ability heuristics related to appeals to emotion:

4. *People are driven to aesthetically enjoy, explore, or endure the design.*

At the level of visual composition, this heuristic is related to Ehses' (2008) pathos strategies, which are themselves associated with aesthetic elements (special arrangements, image and color choice). Nielsen's recommendation of minimalist aesthetics (Nielsen, 1995) is only suitable if it is the best strategy in a particular rhetorical situation. In the majority of situations other aesthetics that elicit positive or negative emotions would be more persuasive. For example, some designs require complex narrative structures or experiences if they are to generate emotional engagement. In a mobile web application designed by the author to promote healthy behaviors (Mejía, 2013), Latino parents showed a strong preference for comic and realistic graphic styles rather than abstracted infographics. This engagement creates an affective response that aids behavior change.

5. *Emotional comfort or friction is generated as a function of the goals.*

There is a tendency to associate pleasurable comfortable emotions with successful design. According to Buchanan (1985), emotional persuasion occurs in the interaction with the object or its contemplation, which should be experienced as fulfilling experiences. For Van der Waarde (2010), in his work on medical pamphlets, pathos-persuasive information should put the patient in the right emotional state of mind, something that European medical information does not do because the relevant European Directive restricts promotional messages, and the experience of opening a pack and unfolding the pamphlets, which contain a large amount of information, is intimidating. Nonetheless, painful emotions that cause emotional friction may be required to achieve the design goals, particularly in social change. For example, some social change viral videos have used sensitive content such as showing how chemical substances may

have reached the milk in the breasts of nursing mothers in order to explain the effects of climate change (Mejía & Longo, 2012). Mejía made use of emotions of shame in gestures made by obese children as a pathos strategy to counter the belief of Latino parents that a healthy child should be chubby (Mejía, 2013).

6. *Symbolism matches audience's culture*

Some symbols are able to carry cultural meanings that generate particular emotional reactions and, hence, may be utilized in design to lead audience to feel desired emotions. According to Aristotle, speakers try to arouse positive or negative emotions in the audience, depending on the rhetorical situation (Aristotle & Kennedy, 1991). The meanings aroused by symbols should be part of the culture, allowing people to make the correct interpretations and, therefore, experience the right emotions. For example, one of the viral videos analyzed by the authors (Mejía & Longo, 2012) used a theme taken from the game of *Monopoly* to visualize a lecture about capitalism. The designer used this theme knowing that the audience was familiar with the symbolism employed and was able to understand it correctly as a metaphor. Another example is the classic use of national symbols that are associated with patriotic attitudes in order to generate emotional effects.

Ethos – credibility

In Aristotle, ethos refers to the credibility of the speaker - not based on his or her reputation but created in the delivery of the speech. The audience projects a profile of the speaker as a preparation for making a judgment. Wisdom (practical sense), virtue (ability to verbalise thoughts), and good will (prudence and fair-mindedness) are the three ethos reasons (Aristotle & Kennedy, 1991). Since in design the speaker is assumed to be the manufacturer, sponsor, or service provider - that is, an entity that is not dynamically “delivering” the design - reputation is a core part of the ethos appeal. Buchanan also emphasized that design products that appeal to ethos are those that show concern and “speak in familiar voices” (Buchanan, 1985, p. 15). Empathic design that understands the feelings and needs of the audience generates credibility appeals. Points 7. to 9., below, constitute a list of the proposed rhetorical ability heuristics related to appeals to emotion:

7. *The reputation of the manufacturer, sponsor, or service provider is visible and clear.*

When clearly apparent in the interaction experience the reputation of the organization or designer will affect the credibility appeal. Van der Waarde's (2010) analysis recognizes this; he concluded that the nature of these medical information texts is ambiguous because patients are not able to distinguish clearly whether the information comes from the pharmaceutical industry, the doctor, the pharmacist, or the regulators. This confusion reduces the credibility of the information. In another example, Mejía used a university logo and technical medical language to strengthen the credibility of a health communication

for Latinos (Mejía, 2013), finding that this information appealed to the ethos of the audience, preparing them to assimilate the information.

8. *The design outcome appears to profoundly understand audience feelings and needs (empathy)*

This is a challenging characteristic for design and evaluation. Design practitioners and evaluators will probably need to know if they are to be able to achieve empathy or be able to assess it. Participatory design, or other qualitative methods should help in this. In one of the viral videos analyzed by Mejía and Longo (2012), for instance, the presenter describes her personal experience with consumer products and lifestyles, which match many feelings in the audience, in order to gain credibility. Recently, Mejía included personal stories of children's characters in a mobile web application hoping to generate higher emotional engagement. He subsequently found during participant interviews that the stories matched stories that were already familiar to participants, which gave high degrees of credibility to the design product (Mejía, 2013). In these examples, empathy was achieved and successfully motivated behavior change.

9. *Neutrality or bias match audience expectations*

In Western audiences where science has a respected status the use of facts or evidence is associated with credibility. This information is considered neutral and the audience considers it to be credible. In political debates biased positions may be expected; for instance, in a right wing party, biased conservative discourses will gain credibility. Mejía and Longo also observed this characteristic in viral videos in which a neutral or biased narrator profile, appearance, and tone are critical for credibility (Mejía & Longo, 2012). For example, in the Story of Stuff video (The Story of Stuff Project, 2007), the presenter uses a calm and neutral tone to explain climate issues and encourage behavior change. This was a successful strategy because the video is not perceived to have a liberal bias.

CONCLUSION

We have developed and explained a list of nine heuristics for use in rhetorical ability evaluation, which are supported by previous design research. The heuristics was developed by paying special attention to the efficacy of design for social change. To correctly use these heuristics, designers and evaluators must have a clear and deep understanding of the rhetorical situation. That is: audience characteristics, context, and the design goal. This understanding will permit the rhetorical ability of a design outcome to be assessed. Thus, the best expert is not an expert in design or rhetoric but rather an expert in the rhetorical situation of the design problem. The main challenge for the expert is to assess whether the design arguments and indices are adequate to the rhetorical situation. To ensure this the expert must note that sometimes

certain “rhetoric-able” outcomes must purposefully hinder cognitive processing (logos) or cause neutrality-bias dissonance (ethos) if they are to be successful in a particular rhetorical situation.

Furthermore, the nine heuristics are not exclusive to logos, pathos, or ethos. Depending on the rhetorical situation, a pathos heuristic may serve to assess logos appeals and so on. For instance, a symbol that does not match audience culture will not only fail to lead the audience to feel the expected emotion (pathos) but will also hinder rational cognitive processing (logos).

This list of heuristics will be tested in our future research agenda with the purpose of developing a specific rhetorical-ability protocol. Such a tool should include recommendations that aid understanding of the rhetorical situation of the design problem and appropriate definitions of the corresponding rhetorical appeal indices.

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RUN FOR YOUR LIFE!

USING EMOTION THEORY IN DESIGNING FOR CONCRETE PRODUCT INTERACTIONS

Steven F. Fokkinga
Delft University of Technology,
✉ s.f.fokkinga@tudelft.nl
Pieter M.A. Desmet
Delft University of Technology,
✉ p.m.a.desmet@tudelft.nl

ABSTRACT

This paper describes a research through design study that investigated the possibility of using emotion theory in the materialization of an interactive product. It is argued that many design for emotion approaches are inspirational and useful in the conceptual phase of a design project, but not in the phase in which concepts are elaborated into final products. The starting points of the study were a design for emotion approach that uses negative emotions to enrich product experiences, and a product that was intended to add engagement to the activity of running by providing users with the experience of being chased. The process of materializing the concept into a prototype, and testing this prototype with participants, was guided by emotion theory. The reflection on this process led to several insights that are interesting for the design of concrete interactions in design for emotion approaches.

KEYWORDS: *design for emotion, research through design, design manifestations, user experience, prototyping*

INTRODUCTION

Imagine it is gam on a Saturday; everything is still quiet outside. The birds are chirping, the sun is gently shining on your face, and you are running for your life. Just before the last corner you were able to shake off your pursuers for a minute, but they have redoubled their efforts and are at your throat again. The warning system on your wrist is counting back to ten meters; seven; four; two. You can hear the heavy breathing right behind you. You only need to get to the end of the street to be safe, but will you make it?

This is the user scenario of a product that was designed to enrich the experience of running. Through different types of feedback provided by a wearable device, runners get the experience of being chased by something. The concept for this product was developed using a theory-driven design for emotion approach, which guides designers in creating richer user experiences by introducing negative emotions into the product interaction (Fokkinga & Desmet, 2013). While developing the concept, the approach and the psychological theory behind it proved to be very helpful in answering design questions such as: What does the experience of running consist of?

Which emotions are beneficial in this context? How could the product evoke such an experience?

However, this approach became much less useful when the concept was taken to the ‘manifestation phase’: the phase in which the product was materialized and the specific interactions were given shape. The relevant design questions in this phase related to more concrete topics like: What shape should the product take? How often should it provide feedback? Which combination of visual, auditory and tactile feedback most successfully evokes the intended experience?

When turning to other sources for inspiration, we found that this gap is characteristic of theory-driven design for emotion and design for experience approaches. Most of these approaches are very useful in the conceptual phase, but do not offer much guidance in manifesting concepts into final products. This means that designers are left to their personal taste, design sensitivity and experimentation to make sure the intended experience is also expressed or evoked by its concrete manifestation. Although this is not necessarily problematic, we think that there is great potential for theory-driven approaches to expand the range of design activities in which they can be inspiring and useful.

In this paper, we describe a project that attempted to use the theory-based ‘rich experience’ approach in the concrete design and testing of a product for runners. By taking a reflective approach during the design and research explorations, we aimed to make a first step towards identifying the factors and challenges of using psychological theory in designing for the manifestation phase. In the following sections, we first introduce the theory-driven approach and the product concept that were the starting points for this project. Then, we explain how the project used the research-through-design method in a way that combined an explicit treatment of psychological and technological variables with a dynamically adjustable prototype. In the following section, we describe the insights we drew from the design and research process. Lastly, we discuss some implications of these insights and the new questions that they raise.

CASE STUDY: DESIGN FOR FEAR EMOTIONS

This project used a theoretical framework that suggests how different negative emotions, if introduced under the right circumstances, can enrich user experiences in several ways (Fokkinga & Desmet, 2012a). This principle is rarely used in product design, but is abundant in the domains of art and entertainment. For instance, shock art, tearjerker movies, and tabloid magazines all make use of different negative emotions (disgust, sadness, and indignation, respectively) to increase their appeal to users. The rich product experience approach derived from this framework was the starting point for the design and research explorations in this project. The approach shows three necessary ingredients for the formation of rich user experiences: the selection of a suitable negative emotion, the elicitation of this emotion through the user-product interaction, and the presence of a ‘protective frame’ (Fokkinga & Desmet, 2013). The selection of the correct negative emotion for the situation is crucial, because each emotion has different effects on experience and behavior. For example, whereas sadness makes people more passive and reflective, anger makes them more active and assertive (e.g., Rucker & Petty, 2004).

In an earlier project, this approach was applied to the context of running. Running is popular in many countries, because it is a sport with a high activity intensity, which at the same time requires little in terms of skills and material investment. However, many runners may experience a lack of enjoyment during running, and as a result have difficulty finding the motivation to run as regularly as they want. It was hypothesized that fear emotions could add thrill, adrenaline and focus to the running experience, which led to the idea of ‘Pursuit’, a product that gives runners the experience of being chased by something as they exercise (see Figure 1).

Fear emotions come in all kinds of shapes and intensities. Although the extreme variants, like fear of spiders or fear of flying, might be the first to be recalled, fear emotions often occur in small, everyday moments. For example, you might experience them when you are unsure of having locked the front door, or when you are afraid of getting your new shoes wet.

Figure 1 - Artist's impression of the Pursuit concept

When properly ‘framed’, fear emotions can have all sorts of pleasant varieties, like the exciting fright when riding a rollercoaster, the suspenseful anxiety when watching a thriller movie, or the invigorating nervousness before giving an important presentation.

Fear emotions can affect user experience in two main ways (Fokkinga & Desmet, 2012a). Firstly, they can directly influence a person’s experience of the world. Scientific studies have shown many such effects: fear causes people to adopt a narrower field of view (Derryberry & Reed, 1998), it makes people experience time as passing more slowly (Tipples, 2011) and people more easily retrieve memories of other times when they were afraid (Bower, 1981). There is also anecdotal evidence concerning the beneficial power of fear from the art world. For example, fiction writer Karen Thompson Walker devoted her 2012 TED talk to arguing that fear has the unique ability to spark people’s imagination, which is apparent in the creative fantasies that people express when they think of their worst fears (“Karen Thompson Walker: What fear can teach us – TED,” 2014). Secondly, fear emotions can change the way we behave and deal with situations, which in turn affects our experience. For example, fear increases adrenaline levels, which gives people more energy to perform physical tasks (Wise, 2009). Tamir and Ford (2009) found that fearful people performed better than people who were positively excited in a game which required them to avoid an enemy. Both the direct experience effect and the behavioral effects can be beneficial for the running context: fear can help people experience their run as more interesting and thrilling, and it might help motivate them to run faster, longer and/or more often.

Obviously, just evoking fear emotions does not necessarily lead to better experiences. After all, fear is often just plain unpleasant. Apter (2007) proposed that the difference between enjoyable fear and unpleasant fear is the presence of a protective frame. Protective frames are psychological constructs that determine whether a person perceives a situation as truly threatening, or as intriguing and exciting. A simple example is a lion in a cage: most people who encounter an uncaged lion

would probably just experience terror. Conversely, encountering a caged lion from close to can change the experience into an enjoyable one. The most important idea is that the cage does not take away the arousal of encountering the lion, but that it makes that arousal enjoyable.

METHOD

According to Zimmerman and colleagues (2010), design research can be grouped into three categories: 1) Research about Design, which investigates design activities and studies how designers work, 2) Research for Design, which aims to create knowledge for designers in the form of frameworks, guidelines and design methods, often by applying or translating knowledge from other disciplines like psychology, and 3) Research through Design, which uses the act of design to iteratively discover what potential future technologies, usage scenarios, and product experiences might look like. From the perspective of this categorization, our project followed a user experience-focused research through design approach, with the ultimate aim of contributing to theory for design (Zimmerman et al., 2010, p. 313).

The research through design process used here was intended to generate knowledge on different levels of specificity. Firstly, it was expected to gain insight into designing for the experience and motivation of running. Secondly, the project aimed to gain more understanding of how negative emotions, and specifically fear emotions, might be elicited during the interaction with a functional product, in such a way that the resulting experience would be more enjoyable and engaging. Lastly, by reflecting on this process in a systematic way, the aim was to generate knowledge on the use of theory in designing concrete product interactions.

The design process and prototyping of the product consisted of two stages. In the first, the hardware prototype was designed and built. The prototype was intended to be a versatile 'platform' rather than a single product, in the sense that it afforded many different types of interaction, which could be altered by exchanging hardware components and adjusting the software. The aim of this approach was to create as

large a 'canvas' of interaction options as possible, which were expected to influence the emotional experience, within the constraints of practical, technical and social feasibility. In the second design stage, these interaction options were explicitly documented as different 'variables'. An example of such a variable was the type of display that the user would carry on their wrist, which came in three varieties: a display with three numbers, a display with a row of bar lights, and a display with a half sphere on top which could display any color in the red, green and blue spectrum (see figure 2).

Examples of other variables included variants based on vibration, shock, and sound stimuli. The different variants of these variables could subsequently be combined into 'experience scenarios'. Each scenario represented a different way in which the product manifested the intended experience effect of the concept. The scenarios were subsequently programmed into the prototype and could be exchanged, and even altered, between testing sessions.

During this stage, iterations were made between several activities:

- Studying literature about the elicitation of different (fear) emotions
- Personal exploration of the possible ways of evoking (fear) emotions
- Design experimentation that explored possible ways of linking (combinations of) concrete interactions to psychological variables

The resulting prototype consisted of two parts. The first part was a small box that runners would put in their pockets, which contained an Arduino system, an accelerometer that measured the runner's speed, and a battery. All the interactions between the runner and the prototype took place through the second part, which runners wore on their wrists. This part provided feedback to the runner through a display, a speaker or headphones, a vibration motor under the wrist, a shock element on top of the wrist (which could administer small electric shocks, far below safety limits), an mp3-module, a synthesizer module, and a large button that could be placed against the runner's body.

Figure 2 - Three display types for the Pursuit prototype

Figure 3 – the Pursuit prototype

The prototype was tested in two-hour sessions with individual participants. Participants (N = 11, 5 female, average age 25.7) were recruited through the university network. In each session, the participant first filled in a short questionnaire about their running style and their motivation for running. After a quick explanation, participants ran with the prototype that was programmed with one of the available scenarios. In most sessions, participants tried multiple scenarios (7 participants tested 3 scenarios, 1 participant tested 2 scenarios, and 3 participants tested 1 scenario). The distance of the runs differed between 2 and 3 km; runs lasted about 10 to 20 minutes, depending on the speed of the runner. During the run, participants wore a cap with an attached video camera that recorded the video and audio of the run from a first-person-perspective (see Figures 4 and 5). Directly after they had finished their last scenario, participants were interviewed about their experiences. During the interview, parts of the recorded videos were watched while the participants retold their experiences, helping them to recall their experiences and compare the different scenarios. This procedure was based on recommendations from the emotion measurement research of Laurans (2011), who found it to offer the best compromise between capturing accurate and rich reports of experiences while intervening as little as possible in the experience itself.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following sections report findings and insights obtained from the research through design process, in which different combinations of interactions were designed and tested using the versatile prototype. Even though the process was iterative, the results are presented in a thematic rather than a chronological fashion, in which each theme represents a constellation of insights. Ten main insight themes are reported, in three loosely defined clusters: (1) lessons learned from the process of developing manifestations of experience; (2) lessons learned from the process of testing manifestations of experience; and (3) additional (general) lessons learned that are relevant for experience design approaches.

Lessons learned from the process of developing manifestations of experience

Emotional granularity

When designing specific emotional interactions for the prototype, one of the first findings was the importance of considering emotions in a high level of 'granularity'. Emotional granularity refers to the amount of detail with which emotions

Figure 4 - The camera cap

Figure 5 - Image captured by the cap during a run

are distinguished (Lindquist & Barrett, 2008). For example, the emotions that are evoked when thinking of a financial problem, when preparing for an exam, or when someone suddenly stands behind you, could all be called 'fear', but might be described with more nuance as 'worry', 'nervousness' and 'startlement', respectively. In that sense, the word 'fear' describes a range of emotions, or an 'emotion family', rather than a single emotion itself (Ekman, 1992). Table 1 provides an overview of the specific fear emotions that were used in the development of the prototype.

These emotions were gathered from several scientific sources (Ben-Ze'ev, 2000; Frijda, 1986; Lazarus, 1991; Ortony, Clore, & Collins, 1988; Wierzbicka, 1999, among others), and selected with the highest amount of granularity that still made sense for designing different interactions. For example, the differences between worry and anxiety (as illustrated in Table 1) were judged as meaningful, and were expected to lead to differently designed interactions. In contrast, although there are also differences between emotions like worry and concern, these were judged to be too insignificant to have an influence on the design strategy – in which case 'worry' was selected to represent both.

Working with the emotions in Table 1 was helpful in three ways. Firstly, their more specific nature was found to be a greater source of inspiration for coming up with concrete interactions. Secondly, they offered a more focused evaluation of the different modes of interaction. For instance, it turned out that certain fear emotions were less effective than others in making the experience enjoyable and that the preference of one fear emotion over another depended on personal preferences. Thirdly, during the design process it was found that, although they belong to the same emotion family, the type of event that elicited them was sometimes very different; indeed, they might even oppose each other. For instance, worry is characterized by long periods of pondering about something that might go wrong, whereas startlement is a very short, visceral reaction to something unexpected. Additionally, nervousness means someone has a certain amount of personal influence over the outcome of a situation, whereas being afraid or anxious means that someone has little or no control. The descriptions in Table 1 were the starting point for the creative process, but were along the way complemented by examples of personal experi-

ences with these emotions, as well as several exercises to find how a product could be altered in order to pass from eliciting one specific emotion to another, which produced additional useful information about these emotions.

In conclusion, these differences between emotions proved to be a fruitful basis for finding answers to more practical questions, such as: Which emotion would be most effective at what point in the interaction? How much control should the user be granted over the interaction? How long should certain episodes last?

Elicitation of fear emotions

Three main ways were found to elicit fear emotions in the user. Firstly, theory suggested that there are certain stimuli which are psychologically 'hard-wired' to evoke fear emotions. Such stimuli included sudden, loud noises, electric shock, frantically blinking lights and 'unreal' noises. Several such stimuli were incorporated into the prototype. Secondly, product interactions could evoke *associations* with real or imaginary fear-inducing things. Interaction elements that made use of associations included angry dog sounds, heartbeat vibrations on the wrist, and supernatural running behavior in the pursuer. Thirdly, interaction elements could be designed using the specific appraisal components of fear emotions. Appraisal components are specific aspects of situations that evoke a certain emotion (Smith & Lazarus, 1993). For example, 'suddenness' is an appraisal component underlying the emotion of startlement. Examples of appraisal components that were useful in the design of the prototype were: (un)expectedness of information, (im)possibility of avoiding certain events, (in)consistency of information, and (in)congruity between interaction elements.

Interaction variables and experience scenarios

These theoretical insights into emotional granularity and the elicitation of emotion (constrained by the technical possibilities of the prototype and the contextual possibilities of running) led to the identification of a number of interaction variables that were expected to have different beneficial effects on the user experience. Figure 6 shows a visual representation of the variables as they were used at the start of the first testing iteration. The squares of the same color represent

Emotion	Definition	Example of an eliciting event
Afraidness	Knowing that a specific bad thing is going to happen	Being afraid of the drill while being at the dentist
Worry	Getting indications of and thinking about something bad that seems likely to happen in the (near) future	Thinking you don't have enough money to last until the end of the month
Nervousness	Feeling that you have to perform well to avert a danger, now or in the near future	Having to do a difficult exam
Startlement	Suddenly being scared by something that wasn't there before	Seeing a pedestrian suddenly step out in front of your car
Confusion	Having the feeling that something is wrong, but not being sure what is happening	Being lost in an big city
Anxiety	The unsettling feeling when things happen that cannot be rationally explained	Hearing an inexplicable noise while alone in the dark

Table 1. – Definitions and examples of specific fear emotions

the different variants of a single variable, such as the type of sound, the mode of the vibration feedback, or the strategy of the pursuer.

Using these variables, ‘experience scenarios’ were created. These were creatively constructed combinations of variables that were expected to evoke a certain emotional experience, or stimulate a different kind of motivation for running. See Table 2 for the four scenarios that were tested in the first round of studies, and Figures 7 and 8 for visual representations of the first two scenarios as combinations of variables. In the tests, small variations were sometimes made to these scenarios in order to test the influence of single variables (e.g. the worry scenario with a beeping sound instead of the voice).

Lessons learned from the process of testing manifestations of experience

Rich experience success criteria

For the user, a rich experience can be defined on the basis of three necessary conditions: a) the experience has to involve at least one negative and one positive emotion, b) the person has to subjectively judge that the experience as a whole has been pleasant or worthwhile and c) the negative emotion has to be felt as a necessary ingredient in that evaluation (as opposed to being an undesired side-effect) (Fokkinga & Desmet, 2012b).

Figure 6 - The interaction variables used in the first iteration

Experience scenario	Manifestation
Worry scenario	The pursuer starts relatively far behind, but is constantly drawing closer, and threatens to catch the runner at the end of the run. The runner gets clear information about this prospect through voice information and the numbered display.
Nervousness scenario	The pursuer is relatively close, and during the run makes several attempts to catch the runner in short sprints which the runner has to be quick enough to avoid. These sprints are announced shortly beforehand. If the runner is caught during one of these sprints, he gets a small shock. The pursuer is represented by dog sounds; the display shows a visual representation of the runner and the distance to the pursuer.
Confusion / Insecurity scenario	The runner only gets very little information, in the form of a beeping sound that becomes increasingly distressing when the pursuer comes closer. There is no visual or tactile information.
Anxiety / Startlement scenario	The pursuer displays unexpected and superhuman behavior, by defying the laws of physics – e.g. being able to run very fast, skipping distances, disappearing and reappearing. At certain times, the pursuer pops up unexpectedly just behind the runner, and the runner has to briefly sprint to outrun it. The runner hears eerie music most of the time and very intense music during the startle moments.

Table 2. - Examples of four experience scenarios and their manifestations

In the tests, different factors emerged that determined whether the prototype was successful in eliciting a rich experience in the user and whether it was successful in motivating them. These factors seemed to work as successive criteria: the prototype succeeded only when all criteria were met. If a certain criterion was not met, the ones succeeding it became irrelevant. First of all, some participants did not accept the basic premise of the concept. In other words, the hypothesized principle of enjoying negative emotions did not apply to them. People in this group sometimes asked whether it was not possible to develop the same concept, but with a more 'positive goal', like chasing something yourself. There were also people who did not want to have their emotions influenced by a product at all. Three (of 11) participants fell into this group. Secondly, some of the participants who did accept the basic premise, sometimes did not like the specific emotions that were evoked for a given scenario. For instance, two participants expressed a liking for the nervousness scenario, but found the emotions evoked in the confusion scenario very unpleasant. In some cases there was also a discrepancy between the effect the emotions had on the experience and the motivation of the runner: one participant said that the worry scenario was the most effective in motivating her to run but that she would not pick it if she had the choice. Thirdly, participants who liked both the concept and the scenario sometimes felt the specific sensory stimuli were unpleasant or did not work. For example, some people found the beeping sound disturbing or frightening, whereas they liked the scenario overall. When each of the three conditions were met, participants expressed a liking for the experience and felt more motivated to run.

Influence of personal running style

Another important factor that determined the effectiveness of the prototype was the personal running styles of different participants, as well as the meaning they attributed to running. Among the participants, roughly three groups emerged. One group of participants (4 of 11) ran mostly to relax or clear their minds, and wanted to be able to run at their own pace. People in this group most often did not use any tools, apps or music during running and were mostly uncharmed by the prototype, or preferred to have a minimal version of it. A second group of participants (3 of 11) ran mostly to improve their performance or to keep fit. People in this group mostly commented on how specific interactions and emotions could help them to improve their performance. A third group of participants (4 of 11) were mostly looking to enjoy a more engaging running experience, and wanted to have more motivation to run. People in this group were most favorable to the prototype, and pointed out that variety in the experience was important to them. Overall, the most insights were obtained from the second group ('functional fear') and the third group ('fear in order to enjoy').

Effectiveness of different emotion elicitations

In the design stage, three different ways were found to elicit fear emotions in the user: hard-wired stimuli, association, and appraisal components. The effectiveness of these different strategies was also found to depend to a great extent on personal

differences. Some participants had strong mental associations with the different stimuli, most notably with the sounds that were used. Several said that the dog sounds not only evoked visual images of dogs, but also stimulated them to construct mental stories that explained why the dogs were chasing them. The abstract beeps evoked widely varying explanations: a mosquito, a ticking clock, a UFO, and the 'sound of darkness'. Other participants had little or no associations with the stimuli, and approached them more functionally. The appraisal components proved more consistent in influencing the experience, although their effectiveness largely depended on the tension between the functional value (see next section) and combinations with other variables (see later section). For instance, the predictability of the pursuer (high in the worry scenario, lower in the nervousness scenario, lowest in the confusion scenario) made a salient difference to the emotions reported by the participants. The hard-wired effects were least successful, with the exception of the shock element, which became an important factor for many participants, one of whom said: 'Although the shock did not feel that bad at all, the idea of being shocked makes a big difference.' The other stimuli -sound, vibration and visuals- were not successful in scaring the user directly.

The tension between functional interactions and engaging experiences

The aim of the design process was to create a product that would evoke certain experiences, but which also had a clear functional aim – to support the user in their running. Three aspects were found during the design and research iterations that made the running experience more engaging but hindered the runner from performing well, and vice versa. All these aspects were in some way related to the control the user had over the product or the experience. Firstly, there was the degree to which the runner had *enough information* to understand what was happening during the run. Especially in the confusion scenario, an important experience factor was to leave the runner relatively in the dark about the whereabouts of the pursuer. For some participants this was effective, and they ran faster as a result. For other participants, not getting enough information was a reason to stop interacting with the prototype altogether, rendering it useless. Secondly, there was the degree to which the runner could *predict* what the pursuer was going to do. A high level of predictability helped runners to plan their run and divide their energy but at the same time it made the experience less novel and engaging. Thirdly, there was the degree to which the runner could *influence* the behavior of the pursuer. Some participants requested the ability to determine when the pursuer was going to sprint. However, the same participants recognized this would also make the experience less effective.

Additional lessons relevant for experience driven design approaches

Holistic combinations of variables

Although too few trials have as yet been carried out to draw a decisive conclusion, it seemed that there was no direct

correlation between single variables and psychological effects. Specific variables, such as sensory stimuli (e.g. beeps) or appraisal components (e.g. ambiguity of information) did not appear, on their own, to influence the type of emotion or experiences. Rather, different *combinations* of variables changed people's experiences with the prototype. For example, participants found the 'worry scenario' quite comforting during the first two thirds of the run if it was combined with a voice announcing the distances run or yet to run, whereas they found the same scenario very 'pressurizing' when it was instead combined with beeps of increasing pitch. In other scenarios, these stimuli had different effects.

Dosage of stimuli

One finding that emerged, which was not fully anticipated in the design phase, was the importance of the proper 'dosage' of certain stimuli over time. For example, vibration was found to have a much more powerful effect on the experience when it was applied moderately (only in the most intense moments) than if it was applied throughout the run. For sound, this dosage seemed to depend mostly on personal taste. Participants who preferred to run without music or aids favored the scenarios that had the least sound, whereas participants who wanted to be entertained while running were conversely annoyed by long silences.

Variation of experience

Another emerging observation was that most people will not have the same (emotional) experience over time if the interaction is not changed. After a while, the same stimuli are less capable of creating the same intensity of experience in the user. For example, a pursuer who is just behind you may be scary during the first minute, but this effect will be lost if it stays at the same distance for the remaining 20 minutes of the run. Two scenarios (worry and nervousness) implicitly remedied this problem in different ways. The worry scenario was relatively static and predictable, but because the pursuer was constantly getting closer, and thus the stimulus became more intense, this scenario was (most of the time) effective until the end. The nervousness scenario, on the other hand, worked because different emotions succeeded each other in time: users first felt nervous anticipation (when they were told the dogs would be approaching soon), then distress (when the dogs were in pursuit), and finally relief (when they had managed momentarily to shake them off), after which the cycle was repeated.

CONCLUSION

This project adopted a research through design approach with the aim of investigating how theory-driven approaches could be useful in the manifestation phase of designing. The approach was a) to use theory to create concrete interactions and b) to design and test explicit combinations of these variables in 'experience scenarios'. This approach was intended to combine the explicit treatment of variables and the clarity of

documentation that characterizes research activities with the ability to make holistic sense of a great number of variables in a creative task, which is typical of design activities.

The outcomes of this approach are promising, although it is still too early to determine whether this type of research will successfully lead to theory-driven approaches that help designers to create concrete interactions. We are currently setting up a second round of design and research activities that follow up on these results. One important, yet difficult, question is to what extent the insights obtained in this study are generalizable. For instance, the study was specifically about fear emotions in the context of running. Are the results also relevant for designers who want to evoke the same type of emotions in completely different user contexts? Or, even more generally, do the results provide useful insights for designers who want to evoke different types of emotions in a different context? More studies in different contexts will have to be carried out to answer these questions. At least one factor that we strongly believe in – but which would have to be confirmed in other studies – is the use of clear and granular descriptions of emotions, motivations and behavior when designing for concrete interactions. We think that specificity and rigor in thinking both have a strong positive impact on the design process and outcome.

We believe that current theory-driven approaches are very valuable for the development of concepts that offer new functions, serve new purposes, or even represent entirely new product categories. However, these approaches offer very few guidelines that assist in choosing a material or in designing a specific interface interaction. There are several reasons why it could be beneficial for theory-driven approaches also to provide knowledge and guidelines for the manifestation phase of design. First of all, many theory-driven product ideas are promising in the conceptual phase but fail to deliver their intended experiences effectively. Although there are obviously many reasons why a promising concept might not turn into a successful product, a mismatch between the experiences that are meant to be evoked by the product concept as such and the concrete design interactions is certainly one of them. Secondly, designers who use experience-driven approaches may become frustrated if they cannot find ways to manifest their concepts successfully, and may end up abandoning such approaches altogether. Thirdly, most consumer products that are developed for the market are not intended to be conceptually novel in their purpose or functions, just incrementally innovative. For the development of such products, designers could benefit from theory that guides them in eliciting certain experiences and emotions through concrete interactions.

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NONVERBAL USABILITY TESTS WITH EMOTIONS FOR THE VISUALLY IMPAIRED

Carlos Henrique Berg, MSc.
Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina
✉ chbplan@terra.com.br

Luciane Maria Fadel, Dra.
Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina
✉ liefadel@gmail.com

Vânia Ribas Ulbricht, Dra.
Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina
✉ vrulbricht@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This paper describes a research-in-progress on the use of onomatopoeias as an alternative form of the EMOCARD. Initially, the theoretical foundations are established in order to identify the most relevant senses when constructing spatial representations for the blind: tactile sense, haptic senses and verbal language. The DECIDE framework was used to define the research subjects, the timing, the research instrument and the evaluation paradigm. The research defined several onomatopoeias for the EMOCARD face images, and all suggestions were recorded to enable an evaluation of the relationship between the images and the onomatopoeias. The research started at the beginning of February 2014, and has been ongoing until now the present moment. Hence, as yet, no conclusions have been reached.

KEYWORDS: *usability test with emotions; spatial representation; onomatopoeias*

INTRODUCTION

Accessibility in Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) is necessary in order to make users feel comfortable, thus, increasing browsing time and encouraging their return to the environment. So that computer interfaces may become more accessible, evaluations are carried out at several different points in time, from the design stage through to implementation and operation. Researchers have at least four paradigms at their disposal for these evaluations (Nielsen, 1999): Specialist Inspections, Computerized Procedures, Heuristic Evaluations and Usability Testing. Of the four paradigms, only usability testing evaluates interaction with the users. The research reported in this article describes an experiment to identify the onomatopoeias that best represent images of emotions. The first usability test was conducted in 2011 using AVEA WebGD, an environment previously evaluated by other paradigms. Twelve blind male/female research subjects (with no other disabilities), participated in the study and, after a period of adjustment, efficiency tests and questionnaires were applied in order to time task execution and user satisfaction (BERG, 2011). A number of barriers were encountered and repaired.

In the search for usability tests with emotions (BERG, 2012), the EMOCARD was identified and used for a new series of

tests. Twelve deaf male/female research subjects (with no other disabilities) were selected. After executing the tasks, seven questions were asked regarding navigation and accessibility in a HCI. Using EMOCARD, barriers regarding colors and the general feeling of the environment were identified (Berg, 2013). These results provided a broader knowledge regarding usability testing with the use of the researchers' emotions.

However, many usability tests of this kind are based on images, which presents a natural barrier for people with visual disabilities. Thus, there is a need to develop tools that allow the visually impaired to participate in usability testing with the use of emotions. Therefore, this paper proposes to determine whether the images of emotions presented by EMOCARD may include versions for the blind, through human feelings. The research question to be addressed concerns the validation of onomatopoeia; "Can onomatopoeias correspond to the emotions encountered in the images of EMOCARD"?

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

By understanding the importance of including persons with disabilities, this study has sought to conceptualize two main

sections that interact and complement one another: tests using emotions and spatial representations. Since the study is focused on testing a method, theoretical questions regarding accessibility and the visually impaired will not be discussed

Tests using Emotions

Salovey and Meyer (1990) contend that emotions are organized responses. Responses occur after crossing the borders of several different systems: psychological, cognitive, motivational and experimental. Emotions typically arise as a response to an event, whether internal or external, and which possess positive or negative valenced meanings (SALOVEY & MEYER, 1990).

Agarwal and Meyer (2009) argue that users have qualitative emotional experiences when they use a product or interface. These emotions are not only central for users to judge the totality of experiences, but can also affect the way users perceive usability (AGARWAL & MEYER, 2009).

For Walker and Prytherch (2008), motivated users demonstrate less anxiety, a greater perception of their self-efficacy and they adopt more positive attitudes. Thus, there is a need to develop interfaces with greater positive emotional responses. To meet this need, models should seek friendliness through emotional interaction, bringing mechanical application interfaces closer to the way in which humans communicate with each other (TZVETANOVA, TANG & JUSTICE, 2007).

The cognitive theory as proposed by Ortony, Clore and Collins (1988) defines emotions as positively or negatively "valenced" reactions to situations, consisting of events, objects and actors. Ancker, Kukafka and Chan (2012) describe emotional responses as negative, positive, or mixed. Moreover, they also claim that in user evaluation, adaptive interfaces exert more positively valenced emotions (TZVETANOVA, TANG & JUSTICE, 2007).

HCI emotional evaluations, using non-verbal methods to identify emotions during a human-computer interaction, are useful for identifying barriers to an interface. Nonverbal tools adopted in order to valence environments were developed by Desmet and Hekkert (2003), who stated that emotions are difficult to verbalize, due to the cognitive effort used to express them. This leads to them losing their content in the same way as a translation process.

Literature review

In 2013, Flores *et al* undertook a systematic literature review involving the most significant papers on the issue of spatial representation in both the blind and the sighted. In the databases - IEEE, SCOPUS; SPRINGER; UFSC Library, CAPES and the Portal Web of Knowledge four combined keywords were employed. The keywords were "blind", "spatial representation", "spatial figure" and "3D", which initially generated 10,823 articles. Following certain constraints, such as "full text", "sanctioned by CAPES", "containing one of the keywords in the title" and "reading the abstracts" demonstrated

relevance and eliminated duplicates, leaving a total of seven relevant articles. Table 2 demonstrates the extracted articles, the first author and the year of publication.

1st Author	Title	Year
AFONSO, Amandine	Structural properties of spatial representations in blind people	2010
HABER, Ralph Norman	Properties of spatial representations	1993
LANDAU, Barbara	Spatial Knowledge and Geometric Representation	1981
LANDAU, Barbara	Spatial Representation of Objects	1989
MILLAR, Susanna	Spatial Representation by Blind and Sighted Children	1976
SCHMIDT, Susanna	Spatial representations in blind people	2012
TESHIMA, Yoshinori	Three-Dimensional Tactile Models	2010

Table 2 – Extracted articles.. Source: Berg and Ulbricht, 2013
The seven studies identified a total of 112 concepts, in which the most frequently identified keyword was "blind" (69). No results were obtained for the keyword "spatial figure". Table 3 indicates the quantities of concepts for four key words identified for each publication.

CONCEPTS	QUANTITY PER ARTICLE							SUB-TOTAL
	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	
BLIND	23	8	14	1	10	3	10	69
SPATIAL REPRESENTATION	16	6	4	0	8	1	5	40
SPATIAL FIGURE	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3D	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	3
TOTAL	39	14	18	4	18	4	15	112

Table 3 – Quantity of concepts identified by author
Note: Haber – A1; Afonso – A2; Schmidt – A3; Teshima – A4; Landau – A5; Landau *et al* – A6 and Millar – A7
Source: the authors, 2013

Spatial Representations

Spatial Representation (SR) is basically the ability of the human brain to use metaphors to build knowledge and to form relationships with the world. The study of SR began with research focused on the psychology of memory in both sighted and blind subjects (HABER *et al*, 1993). According to Afonso (2010), spatial representation appears to include valid metric information, and studies consistent with Haber *et al* (1993) have demonstrated that representations made by children incorporate certain geometric properties.

Studies in other areas of cognition have revealed a rich system of spatial knowledge in blind children (LANDAU, 1989). A review of Landau, Spelke and Gleitman (1984) encountered evidence regarding knowledge of spatial layout. The study also revealed haptic skills and spatial representations of objects that went beyond simple maps (LANDAU, 1989), as well as an excellent knowledge of spatial language.

From the viewpoint of Berkeley (1993), haptic patterns or exploratory motor coordination serve as a basis for the unified development of the spatial representations of objects. Landau (1989) corroborates this idea when he argues that blind children naturally develop haptic exploratory activities, which allow them to extract important information from objects. Teshima (2010) believes that the blind are able to recognize three-dimensional shapes through haptic sensations. Moreover, this not only involves visual information, but also the use of haptic sensations, which help to improve recognition in 3D, thus enabling the construction of SR from objects.

The implications of using different strategies to process spatial information are important when spatial information is obtained from spoken language, as is often the case in the blind (SCHMIDT *et al*, 2012). Millar (1976) assumes that the differences in spatial representation cannot be inferred because it is necessary to adopt a verbal strategy rather than strategic imagery to process the information available, as in the case of the blind.

However, research has demonstrated that representations made by children incorporate certain geometrical properties (HABER *et al*, 1993), as well as evidence of the knowledge of spatial layout (LANDAU, SPELKE & GLEITMAN, 1984). The main elements for generating SR include valid metric information (Afonso, 2010), haptic skills and spatial representations of objects (LANDAU, 1989).

Haptic Sensations

The haptic system is the result of tactile-kinesthetic coordination efforts made during exploratory acts, primarily used in the manipulation of objects with the aim of detecting size, shapes, textures, etc. (MAUERBERG-DECASTRO, 2004). Ochaita and Rose (1995) presented the haptic system or active touch, as the most important sensory system for the blind to discover the world. The authors make a distinction between the haptic proprioceptive and the haptic visual systems. The first provides fluency to coordinated actions through joint muscle synergies. The second key aspect of this approach relates to the immediate postural responses during action (and at rest) (i.e., low-order system).

Then, there is the visual system that, in addition to the underlying functions of the haptic system, detects depth because of binocular disparity, motion parallax, texture gradient and shadows (ATKINS, FISHER & JACOBS, 2001). Finally, the haptic visual system does not replace the haptic proprioceptive system, it acts at a high-order level that guides movements towards the visualized targets.

Based on these studies, touch becomes more important for the formation of SR, especially since it contributes to the construction of mental maps and geometric shapes. The study also brought to light the importance of haptic sensations in this composition.

Onomatopoeias

One of the problems with research is the limitation of usability tests including emotions that use images, which clearly creates barriers for people with visual impairments. In the pursuit of solving this problem, research conducted on spatial representations in the blind have identified touch and haptic sensations as the main sources for the development of SR. It is assumed that even sound stimuli compose haptic sensations (MILLAR, 1976).

The use of spoken language is also indicated as a component for the creation of SR. Therefore, in order to develop adaptations of usability tests including emotions, such as Emocard, for use by people with visual impairments, touch may be considered as a way to recreate the tool. However, a second approach may be based on spoken language. The limitation of language, in this case, is the same as indicated in cases of verbal usability tests, and cognitive effort is required to translate and understand its meaning and content, and onomatopoeia may be used.

Onomatopoeic sound reproduction is in the form of phonemes and, in general, they are universally understood. Animal sounds, noises, screams and sounds of nature or machines can replace the name (verb) or the SR of any particular thing. Table 4 demonstrates some examples:

ONOMATOPOEIA	EXAMPLE
Boom	Onomatopoeia of an explosion
Moo	Onomatopoeia of a cow
Vrum	Onomatopoeia of an accelerating car
Aiii	Onomatopoeia of pain (Portuguese)

Table 4 – Examples of onomatopoeia
Font: the authors, 2014

Developing a tactile model implies high costs and long waiting periods, and considering its importance, this model should be explored in depth in further articles. In this study, the onomatopoeic perspective will be addressed through the low costs involved and the facility with which the model may be developed.

Hence, between September and December 2013, a survey was conducted among graduate Design students at the Universidade Federal do Paraná and Engineering and Knowledge Management students at the Universidade, totaling twenty-nine research subjects. Subjects were shown a table containing eight emotions from the Emocard in the form of illustrations. Research subjects were requested to suggest onomatopoeias for each of the emotions listed.

	Distress	Displeasure	Depression	Slipiness	Arousal	Relaxation	Pleasure	Excitement
aaaah	humf	oh	hm	oh	zii	heheh	haha	
aaaah	HUMPF	Ooow	hmm	oh	zzz	HEHEHE	haha!	
aarr	humpf	oum	hmm	oh	zzzz!	hehehe	HAHAHA	
Aff.../ Grr...	hunf	ouuu	hmmm...	OH!	zzzzz	hehehe	hahaha	
ah!	hunf	ow	HUM	oh!	zzzzz	hehehehe	Hahaha!	
ahhh	hunf		humm	ohh		hihi	Hahaha!!!	
ahhhh			HUMM	ohh		hihihi...	hahaha...	
ahhhh...			Hummm...	ohhhh			hahahah	
AHHHHH			huuum	OHHHH			hahahah	
			nnnnn	ooh			HAHAHA	
			uhmmm	oohh			hahahaha	
			un	OOHH			HAHAHAH	
			un...	ooo			lahahaha	
			unhh	ooh			kkkkk	
				ooh			kkkkkk	
				ooh			kkkkkk	
				OOH!!!			kkkkkkkk	
				óóóó				
				oooo				

Table #5 - Images, words and onomatopoeias
Source: adapted from Desmet, 2003

The responses generated a map with 89 different onomatopoeias, where the most similar were grouped for recording. Table 5 presents the images of the Emocard emotions, the name selected for the emotion and the onomatopoeias selected for recording.

With this information, similar onomatopoeias were grouped, and in conjunction with an audio producer, the onomatopoeias to be recorded were defined. The onomatopoeias were recorded one by one in an audio studio, in male and female voices for testing.

Methodology

This was a qualitative research that sought initial information concerning the problem. The DECIDE framework, as proposed by Preece, Rogers and Sharp (2002) was used to structure the research. DECIDE is the acronym for:

- Determine the goals,
- Explore the questions,
- Choose the evaluation paradigm,
- Identify the practical issues,
- Decide how to deal with ethical questions and
- Evaluate.

The goal was to verify whether the recreation of the Emocard tool using onomatopoeias may be recognized. The question

to be addressed concerned validation of the onomatopoeia. The research question was: "Can onomatopoeias correspond to the emotions encountered in the images of EMOCARD"?

The evaluation paradigm was a questionnaire. Validation was conducted by comparing the recorded onomatopoeias with the images from the EMOCARD. The evaluation was carried out by numbering the Emocard with the number of onomatopoeias that most resembled the emotion. As a research tool, an answer sheet was created for responses. An identification profile of the research subject was placed at the top informing gender, age and graduate program. Below this, for each voice type, an Emocard was printed in order to mark the answers. Illustration 1 presents a facsimile of the search tool.

Practical issues refer to defining the research subjects and the manner of applying the research. With regard to the research subjects, the Nielsen and Loranger (2007) recommendations were observed, by using five to twelve research subjects. The reasons for using this number of subjects were related to costs (LORANGER & NIELSEN, 2007), and the implementation schedule (PREECE, ROGERS & SHARP, 2002), so as to avoid a repetition of the results (NIELSEN & LORANGER, 2007). Thus, once the mapped recommendations were met, two groups were selected: one male and one female, made up of post-graduate students.

Figure 1 – Research tool facsimile.
Source: adapted from Desmet, 2003

The study was applied using the following steps:

1. Presentation of the research objectives and methodology
2. Presentation of the research tool to the research subjects
3. Playing all onomatopoeias, twice, with one short interval
4. Playing each onomatopoeia individually three times
5. Period for annotation of the onomatopoeia on the Emocard
6. Playing other onomatopoeias, one by one, repeating steps 3 and 4.
7. Collecting cards, thanks and finalization of the study.

Finally, in relation to ethical issues, researchers informed the research subjects that the object of evaluation was the tool and not themselves. It was also made clear that anonymity would be maintained, and that only information regarding gender, age and post-graduate study would be requested.

After collecting the cards, results were tabulated, and thus the number of recognitions for each onomatopoeia was identified.

RESULTS

The scientific lens of this research aimed to present the current situation of evaluating the human-computer interface of virtual learning environments. The usability test of the EMOCARD emotions was introduced for this type of assessment and knowledge regarding spatial representation in the blind.

Knowledge concerning spatial representations defined the sensations that the blind use: touch, hearing and the haptic - the component of spatial representations. Ochaita and Rose (1995) also demonstrated that, regardless of disability, the blind construct spatial representations in the same way as the sighted, but using other strategies.

This study used onomatopoeias, the representation of sound in the form of phonemes, which are generally universally understood. Based on the EMOCARD, the post-graduate students proposed onomatopoeias for each of the eight emotions, which were ordered, grouped and recorded in the studio with male and female voices.

The onomatopoeias were tested in March 2014, with the participation of six females and four males, and tabulated. Tabulation enabled us to verify and validate the onomatopoeias that represented the images of EMOCARD emotions. The most cited onomatopoeia was the one referring to “relaxation”, and it was recognized six times. “Sleepiness” received five recognitions and “arousal”, four. “Distress”, “excitement” and “pleasure” were recognized respectively by three, two and one subjects. “Depression” and “discontent” were not recognized by any subject.

Differences in perception were noted between men and women. “Affliction” was recognized only by women and “excitement” only by men. “Relaxation” and “sleepiness” received the same number of recognitions amongst males and females. The other onomatopoeias, due to few recognitions, did not permit evaluation.

As an exploratory research, this study has allowed us to answer the question “Can onomatopoeias correspond to the emotions encountered in the images of EMOCARD”? The statement is partially true because two onomatopoeias were recognized by most subjects and, with the exception of “depression” and “discontent”, all presented some kind of recognition.

At this point, the research should set out to follow two paths. The first: to increase evaluations to a statistical level. The second: to develop onomatopoeias, so that those which remained unrecognized may become recognizable.

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GET ON BOARD! EDUCATIONAL DESIGN FOR EARLY CHILDHOOD, APPROACHED AS INTERDISCIPLINARY PARTICIPATION.

Diana C. Casalins Petro

Head of Education Department. Parque Cultural del Caribe. Museo del Caribe.

✉ dcasalins@culturacaribe.org

Ketty Miranda Orozco

Research Coordinator Graphic Design Program. Universidad Autónoma del Caribe.

✉ kmiranda@uac.edu.co

Tatiana Miranda Orozco

Educational Projects Professional. Parque Cultural del Caribe. Museo del Caribe.

✉ tmiranda_88@hotmail.com

ABSTRACT

Museums continue to be communication centers serving as a channel for different societies to deliver and communicate their cultural traits to future generations. Education, museology and design teams are challenged to develop experiences that facilitate learning, often realizing that the parameters followed to design them do not match users' expectations. Through a process of exploring various sources: exhibitions offered at museums, non-experts expectations, and the participation of designers, the design of educational materials for early childhood was developed to meet the needs of users and aiming to democratize the design process in order to achieve relevant results that respond to the context as well as create and structure a methodology which could be replicated in other centers.

KEYWORDS: *museums, early childhood, interdisciplinarity, light-shadow, experience design.*

INTRODUCTION

While today the role of museums has expanded to the conscious action of educating, communicating and transmitting information, some of their historic tasks prevail. The museum remains a communication center, serving as a channel for different societies to deliver and communicate their cultural traits to future generations. Therefore, preserving the diverse cultural content, in a cyclic spiral in which knowledge is not only transmitted to the young, but is enriched through the process and creates new knowledge. From the beginning, although sometimes they don't intend to, museums constantly build memories and versions of societies. They appear to convey a past, but what they do is build representations of the past, and those representations always respond to the present they are created in (Jaramillo, 2008).

Although originally museums were not created to consider school visitors, school visits are becoming more frequent, with the aim to enhance or provoke additional study of certain aspects of the children's learning. Given this reality, museums have seen the need to renew and remove their structures to go beyond the custody and collection, to make their exhibitions acquire new meanings for their new audiences.

Museums, zoos and science centers, constitute natural spaces for exploration and informal learning. Free-choice learning experiences are of great importance, considering that on average, formal education covers only 3% of an average person's lifespan (Falk and Dierking, 2002). One of the priorities for informal learning institutions, is to provide experiences that have value in and of themselves, so visitors choose to engage in learning activities because they find them inherently satisfying (Lane, 2014).

According to Altman (1998), visitors rarely stop to read the signs, and for museum, zoo and science center education teams, it is important to ask about the impact of resources displayed, namely, if visitors read the labels that the education team has carefully designed for them and whether the messages are reaching the audience. Staff at zoos, museums and science centers has different perspectives about what visitors want, like or dislike. But the question about whether those ideas are based on reality remains open (Schram, 2011). Very often experienced designers face user' expectations and perceptions which do not always concur with their own.

This article communicates the process of research and design of the educational experience named Get on Board! Design for Museo del Caribe's early childhood education portfolio, in which

the interests and expectations of parents, teachers, artists and professionals from other disciplines were used as input to guide the work of the museums' design and education teams.

WHY DESIGN FOR EARLY CHILDHOOD AT A MUSEUM?

"Every society, every culture and every era explicitly or implicitly defines childhood, its characteristics and, consequently, the periods of life it includes. Therefore, it is important to understand that our concept of children is socially constructed, arises from our expectations, and children are not children "naturally", but in fact, from a historical perspective, the consideration of children as a different social category, is a very recent creation." (Ancheta, 2008).

In the current Colombian context, since the creation of the Early Childhood Public Policy in 2006, it has been stated that the child is a unique being, with an active and expansive persona, biological, psychological, social and cultural specificity. Born with sophisticated capabilities and quickly developing better tools to think, process and transform the information they receive from their environment and learning very rapidly the relationships existing within the family and in all social environments they live in. Early childhood is a very important stage in the life of every human being, it is a period in which reorganization and permanent transformation of skills are carried out and for that reason, will demand meaningful experiences that foster knowledge about real world, from others and for themselves (MEN, 2009).

As declared by Janette Griffin, "it is vital for museums, to bring young visitors memorable experiences, because this influences their future contracts with cultural opportunities. Good and early experiences determine their own attitudes on participation they will later hold together with their families and friends. And this is what our version of the butterfly effect is about. Translated, this metaphor means: small flapping, meaning, memorable experiences in museums, which perhaps may have great impact on the future life of those who experience them" (Quoted by Alderoqui, 2008).

METHODOLOGY

We implemented a methodological design which allowed us to discover ideas from the perspective of a small sample of teachers, parents, psychologists, artists, educators and designers (who in their practice, had frequent personal and professional contact with children under 6 years), about the activities and educational materials considered "ideal" for early childhood.

Qualitative research provides more depth and richness of data, given that it is produced by different stakeholders, from different sources, and by using a greater variety of forms of data collection (Sampieri, 2006). This led us to proceed with the active participation of researchers gathering information through:

1. Survey and analysis of organizational documents and materials describing the range of early childhood activities and resources, available in 52 museums.
2. Polling via surveys to 32 non-experts in design (parents, teachers, psychologists and artists who work with infants) on current practices and expectations about the activities and resources available in their context.
3. Review of group artifacts created by non-experts in design for the purpose of this study at the working sessions, in order to establish trends and principles of the expected activities for early childhood.
4. Log the creation process of artifacts, by design experts for the purpose of this study, following the guidelines emerging from the analysis of the sessions with non-expert participants.

It was expected that the analysis of these four sources would allow us to explore the current state of experiences museums offer to an early childhood public and, by these means, to spot trends and potential problems versus expectations of non-experts, to formulate a strategy that subsequently integrates experts and non-experts through a model of co-creation and interdisciplinary work, systematizing the experience and allowing it to be replicated in other contexts and situations.

CURRENT MUSEUM OFFER

Museums and science centers play an important role in the construction of imaginaries and generating space for meaningful learning; however, just in the last 20 years, new initiatives have emerged in museum design aimed at early childhood, an audience which is particularly diverse and one on which museums and science centers had not focused before.

In the words of Dufresne-Tasse (2008) the museum educators became interested in pre-school children to the extent that educational services diversified their offer to older ones. Following this course, educators developed programs, exhibitions and even museums characterized by maximum use of "interactivity", designed for little children, sometimes looking to entertain through exhibits but, above all, intended to complement the children's psychomotor development or introduce them to the world of art and science.

"Recent experience in several countries shows how the same contemporary museum users (children, youth and adults alike) demand a versatile offer which allows them, through exploring the museum, to be in touch with an inspiring opportunity for knowledge, a possibility to be entertained and a high level leisure experience or in a different order, an experience where you can unleash your creativity from various stimuli" (Orozco, 2005,).

However, the following design trends and the specific offer for younger children, often reflect a lack of scrutiny and use

1 Author's translation

of contextual elements to enhance cultural experiences. It is understood that an educational space is significant when it comes to any situation, activity, task, problem or cultural practice which provides them with the opportunity to learn, reassemble their skills and actually requires them to "think" (MEN, 2009).

Through reviewing the current offer for early childhood, in museums around the world, some trends were quickly spotted. Listed below are the most common:

1. Thinking about children does not always imply early childhood:
Some museums have a range of activities for children starting at school age (5 or 6 years and older). A typical activity involves themed tours, which require the company of adults, language processing and other features hindering autonomous exploration or not exploiting the interests of younger children by touching, smelling, biting, etc. (Example: thematic tours for children at the Louvre Museum)
2. Stories at the museum:
There is a trend in museums to associate activities for children with story reading sessions. The advantage of this type of activity is that many museums allow these youngsters (18 months old) to participate in the company of their parents (Example: MET Museum Family Programs).
3. Touch, smell, listen:
With growing awareness of children's needs, activities have been created that focus on the senses: sight, touch, smell, taste, etc. The advantage of these sensory activities is the variety of opportunities that are presented to the children. The disadvantage is represented by the need to create an alternative space or special exhibits to allow free exploration for children through the various objects and proposed materials (Example: Kids and families MOMA lab).
4. Children tours:
Many museums often provide accompanied visits for children, which are basically interpretations aiming to bring smaller groups to ask questions about the collection pieces. An advantage they offer is the use of non-complex language and the fact that they allows small groups to view the collections. One of the disadvantages is that these visits are not always available for smaller groups because of the difficulties this represents (Example: Thyssen Bornemisza Dynamic visits).
5. Role-play:
Role-play is found fairly often and generally a mediator guides participants who are given an assignment. These activities present the advantage of allowing children to enjoy the experience and gain knowledge of a specific topic. On the downside, many of these games can only be played by children over 5 years, or even children who can read or write, which refers back to the idea of "Thinking about children does not always imply early childhood."

(Example: Natural History Museum UK Wildlife garden explorers).

Figure 1. Groups participating on the ideation sessions used diverse materials to create prototypes.

CALL FOR STAKEHOLDERS: IDEATION AND DESIGN GUIDELINES

The second part of the project was a co-creation. More than any other type of visitor participation, co-creative projects challenge institutional perceptions of ownership and control of content. Co-creative projects require "radical trust" in community members' abilities to perform complex tasks, collaborate with each other, and respect institutional rules and priorities. To execute a successful co-creation project, staff members must not only trust the competencies and motivations of participants but deeply desire their input and leadership (Simon, 2010). Co-creation has proven to be successful in other projects at different Museums, connecting users' needs with staff responsible for developing programs, activities and exhibits in Museums.

After the initial survey of resources available at the museums, we proceeded to make a call to parents, teachers, psychologists and artists in the local community close to the Museo del Caribe. Using a sampling by network through museum visitors' database, a group of 32 participants was assembled. The shared condition was to be in permanent contact with children under 6 years.

The sessions' objective was to explore expectations and imaginaries about the ideal characteristics of activities and resources for children, as well as participants' perceptions about the museum's exhibits for children in this age range. Once the group was selected and their participation confirmed, the session was held, communicating its purpose, and developing exercises to create artifacts.

Through analysis of the session, the prototypes (Figure 2.) designed by participants and the answers to the proposed questions, a draft of guidelines was created to meet the expectations expressed by the participants at the ideation lab. These design guidelines became the foundation for designing educational experiences.

Design Guidelines:

- **Experiencing stories:** this refers to the need to explore the development of a resource to promote reading processes; it becomes an excuse to enhance storytelling, role-playing around folk tales, and narration of everyday and traditional stories.
- **Playfulness:** the experience should be attractive to children, presented in a way that facilitates exploration, enjoyment, play, and contact with the arts. Less relevant are content and knowledge.
- **Production:** both parents and educators agree on “crafting” as an essential action. Thus, experience should facilitate the production of artifacts and handling of materials like paints, clay, paper, wool, among others, to promote artistic creativity in children.
- **Multisensory:** learning from the use of senses is a priority. Those materials encouraging exploration and using the senses: sight, touch, smells, textures, color, lights are important to develop at this stage of life.
- **Structured Space:** this refers to the interest manifested by both parents and educators to rely on a physical space at the museum, where the educational activities offered to children can take place. This includes the building of an appropriate infrastructure, adequate to meet the specific characteristics of children under 5.
- **Short Activities:** activities are expected to last a maximum of 30 minutes in order to keep children’s attention and motivation.

These guidelines identified the need to facilitate experiences that demand multisensory exploration. Humans are sensory by nature and it is through the senses that learning becomes meaningful. So, as explained by Zapata and Ceballos: “Education in early childhood cannot be based on mechanical, repetitive, meaningless activities that seek only one-way information transmission (from the adult to the boy-girl) with little meaning and motivating. For this reason, the terms initial education or early childhood education comes from a

Figure 2. Prototypes were analyzed to define guidelines. This picture shows a spatial proposal to an activity, which was supposed to use light on glass walls. Participants rated their favorite designs with sticky notes.

broader concept, which aims to overcome the limited vision of education associated with schooling, and seeks to fill with meaning the daily lives of children, contributing to their development as human beings and promoting their free expression and construction of learning” (2010).

TEAMWORK: EXPERIENCE CO-CREATION

Once consultations and examinations were carried out, the next step was creation. In this phase, graphic and industrial design professionals, psychologists and the Museo del Caribe education team were invited to participate. The aim at this stage was to assemble an interdisciplinary team in order to design the experiences. The experience creation model leads to working across disciplines, but also to work that obeys to different requirements, scenarios and knowledge, with groups that rarely interact with each other in discussions about the design of educational activities.

Guidelines suggested the creation of experiences over merely materials, then, the designers faced the challenge to develop these, with a sense of interaction aesthetics, since not only the materials, but also their use needed to be carefully crafted. The term “interaction aesthetics” to refer to the qualities of a design that lead to the feelings, emotions, and the behaviors that result from these more bodily types of interactions. An important element of these types of interactions is that they happen over time. This is why when we talk about interaction design, and user experience design it is important to not forget that interactions and experiences happen over time (Eden, 2014).

Once again, the co-creation model was followed. Co-creative projects allow cultural institutions to form partnerships that are responsive to the needs and interests of their audiences. Of course, visitors walk into museums with their own needs and interests every day. When staff members are attentive to and interested in accommodating these needs, they can design programs to invite visitors to use the space for their own

Figure 3. Teams focused on different topics and mediation strategies. The group of teachers portrayed here, proposed a room full with objects for children to play their favorite stories.

reasons without entering extensive co-creative partnerships (Simon, 2010).

With guidelines resulting from the analysis in phase, 4 activities were proposed and design teams had the task of creating specific material in order to meet the needs expressed by parents and professionals, framed in the educational philosophy of the Museo del Caribe and adding value to the trends identified in other museums around the world. By translating the guidelines in design and functional prototypes, the next step was taking new material to the production stage. The activities proposed through the call to the design teams were:

1. *Paint your route*: An ephemeral space becomes a field exploration and creation. This activity required the creation of a maze of variable dimensions, which could be assembled inside and outside the museum, allowing children to enter and exit painting the walls with Caribbean colors and the shapes of their imagination.
2. *Animal Enigma*: Caribbean animals are used to ignite a visual exploration of a colorful mural. This experience takes place in a particular space, where light reflected on the wall is controlled, and allows different animals to become visible. The objective of this experience refers to the visual exploration of little children, supported by their parents, while animals appear and disappear in a game of light and colors.
3. *Melquiades' Secrets*: Directly from the confines of Macondo, children receive a visit from Melquiades, a character with a backpack loaded with curious and magical items, for them to look at, touch, smell and feel. A retrieval of the atavist characters of grandfathers and travelers, who come together to share with the little ones and their parents stories of adventure in the nearby Caribbean.
4. *Get on Board! Water, light and color*. Three key elements underpin an experience in which little children approach the tradition of folk stories and legends through a set of magic lanterns and shadows cast on the backdrop and the theater of river, sea and water stories.

EXPERIENCE DESIGN: GET ON BOARD! CASE STUDY.

In response to the call made by Museo del Caribe, students and professionals from different disciplines attended to design and create educational materials. The Universidad Autónoma del Caribe Graphic Design Program, participated through the research group Ellipsis on the design of the “Get on board!” activity aiming to contribute to appropriation and valuing the Colombian Caribbean’s natural and cultural heritage. The research group hosted the project in the Culture Society and began to work on the development of document reviews, interviews, Museo del Caribe visits and teamwork, as well as the developmental stage previous concept design for graphic pieces in order to contextualize the project under the Caribbean historic heritage.

It is important to implement initiatives for early childhood aimed at strengthening their identification with the historical cultural heritage, which we are part of, are defined by and build on a daily basis. From the research group Ellipsis, identity was understood using the theoretical contributions of Jamaican thinker Stuart Hall, which defines culture beyond the functional concepts that conceive it as a set of practices, behaviors, institutions or social processes, to come to place it in the context of meanings and communication. It is established as well that a learning environment needs the design of cultural artifacts. Among these we find: the symbolic frame or context, discursive genre and language use, educational resources, materials and timeframe in which activities are carried out (Zamora, 2000).

The countries’ flora and fauna offer an exuberant text, provoking great pleasure (Zamora), along this line of thought, an educational experience in which children could get on board at the Caribbean was designed, through stories set around the most important rivers in the Colombian Caribbean: Cayman Man (Magdalena River), The Hurtado mermaid (Guatapurí River), The golden fish (Cauca River) The Tofeme Corcovado (Rio San Jorge) and Zenú Domicó (Sinu River) all these known through folk stories. This theme was chosen in order to encourage children’s Caribbean identity through oral traditions. As declared by Hall (1996), identities are narratively constructed from, first, the stories told by people about who they are and where they come from, based on their historical experience and, on the other hand, the practical use of these stories to build the future.

Moreover, reading is a natural process in the development of human intellectual skills. However, educators must change some mindsets that make them establish the text formed by conventional graphic symbols (letters) as the only one, unaware that the human being, from his early life, is able to interpret signs and different message codes: auditory, body color, movement, light and shadow (Zamora).

One of the challenges faced when designing the educational material, was the search for new ways to sensitize target audiences, because the purpose was to develop funny mi-

Diseño de material educativo para enseñar a la primera infancia Historias del Caribe Colombiano entorno al Agua.

Figure 4. Logo designed for the experience Get on Board! Reflecting the purpose to jump into the activities and river stories on the Caribbean.

cro worlds, making learning dynamic by focusing on a type of design which allowed users to exceed the role of passive consumers, as affirmed by Bejarano (1997) "We are part of a culture within which we easily become visual imagery, but not mental devourers." Hence, the interest to offer an experience for thinking, imagining and sensing. "To favor intelligent development means helping to understand the surrounding reality, offer possibilities of play, allow touching, act, test, experiment ... " (Zamora).

The target audience for this experience was children between 0 and 6 years old, characterized for using their senses as channels to understand reality and the world around them. The texts' pluriperception is rich in the first years, then offering a stimuli enriched medium will be fundamental to develop reading skills (perception, interpretation, reflection and response) framed in the world of emotional and symbolic abundance of the early years (Zamora). Thenceforth "Get on board!" became a multisensory experience, which proposes a strategy for image based reading, where light, shape and color become the stars. The experience was designed to give rise to different sensations in the children through dynamic of exploration and creation, implying creativity, imagination and discovery motivating children to think and collectively create stories. This, in turn, stimulates reading capabilities. Infants younger than four months, only perceive images as shadows, they see in black and white, and from this moment on they develop their macula and visual cortex definition. This continues to develop until they are seven years old (Zamora).

In this experience, children have fun recreating a story with the help of light pipes (flashlights) and lenses projecting lights and shadows on a wall, which becomes a canvas where these are cast. Get on Board! Uses light as a design element. It has been proven that the appropriate use of light can lead to a more pleasurable experience (Arefian Atelier, 2011). Every child has access to a tube with a set of interchangeable lenses that can project the icons from the stories created for "Get on board!" These icons are chosen as the story evolves. Each lantern has the following dimensions: body height body and lid: 22.8 cm; flashlight body: 21.4 cm, lens height: 7.7 cm. And every black and white silhouette lens has a diameter: 7 cm.

Figure 5. Light-pipe prototype with some of the first set icons ready to be tried and projected.

The production of lanterns and lenses followed requirements for resistance, safety and usability for kids. This means they were produced using a durable material, which is washable and resistant to water, humidity, smashing and manipulation by children. The materials used include carton and acrylic, which are non-toxic. The final artifact avoids sharp, abrasive or puncture wounds and the size of the lens is big enough to ensure that no airways are obstructed by foreign bodies. No electric charge is required when in use, except a low voltage batteries adaptor, which is not in direct contact with the surface. Finally, it is a proper ergonomic flashlight, well matched to the psychomotor stage for small children, in terms of being maneuverable and lightweight.

Human communication started with images, progressed to pictographs, went to phonetic units and finally to the alphabet. According to Costa (2003), signs and symbols have the ability to evoke absent things, which are not present in the message –but implicitly meant. The icons are conventional figurative representations, which use familiar images easily recognizable. They were widely used in times when people "could not read or write". Young children read icons from an early age (Zamora). The phenomenon (Figure/Ground) captures the idea that in perceiving a visual field, some objects take a prominent role (the figures) while others recede into the background (the ground). The visual field is thus divided into these two basic parts (Soesgaard, 2014).

"Get on board!" encourages children to read signs of the Colombian Caribbean region. Icons representing different characters from the stories are printed on the lenses (for example, the Hurtado mermaid, Cayman Man, etc.) as well as the fauna, flora and objects mentioned in folk stories, and with them the legends proposed by the interpreter are represented.

It is for this reason that the strategy to approach the target audience was through image reading, since in early childhood, children are just beginning to learn written language. Reading competencies are stimulated, not just by typographic acknowledgment, but as mentioned by Bello and Holzwarth (2008), though different literature related activities, for example, when teachers show images, tell stories, asking children to recreate them through images or encouraging them to create their own by questioning the pictures.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Using an iterative and co-creative design process allows exhibits to be refined and readjusted. Defining clear goals and objectives, which are connected with curricula and other relevant schemes enables ideas and content to be evaluated and adjustments to be implemented (CAVE, 2010).

Through the proposed methodology, it was possible to obtain relevant information about expectations and perceptions of parents and teachers of children under 6 years, which allowed designers and educators to use adequate strategies to address the audience's needs. Similarly, conducting surveys

on the practices of other museums for the same audience, informed the team about the opportunities and challenges existent in the field.

As a result, a methodology was structured, aiming to integrate the participation of experts and non-expert stakeholders, in the design process of educational resources for early childhood, democratizing the project participation through co-creation process, enriching it with new perspectives from different disciplines, linking content and mediation strategies to context needs and characteristics.

The resulting experience from “Get on board!” will help to ignite reading competencies in children under 6, through experimentation with light, color, shadow and storytelling, in a space of fun multisensory stimuli. It is clear that educational opportunities promoting verbal and non-verbal communication skills cannot be delayed until the beginning of schooling. Linguistic capabilities, when properly stimulated in early childhood, favor more skills to be developed in the future stages. Intelligent reading processes promote world building and reconstruction through play, interaction and human soul gratification.

One of the most important findings for the team, was understanding that for this specific audience, content was irrelevant, otherwise it resulted much more important to prioritize the multi sensorial dimension experience according to perceptive conditions for young children. This finding provided working guidelines to designers. We suggest to incorporate different sources to survey user needs in activities design projects, in order to keep obtaining this kind of insight, which may already be available in literature, but sometimes keeps being ignored by design teams, in their attempt to produce sophisticated experiences. We suggest the replication of this exercise in order to consolidate and adjust the methodology and study additional practices to stimulate interaction of different stakeholders to facilitate future design processes, responding to the challenges presented by users’ expectations and contextual needs reinforcing identity processes in order to achieve meaningful learning in cultural topics.

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EXPERIMENTING WITH MATERIALS – A SOURCE FOR DESIGNERS TO GIVE MEANING TO NEW APPLICATIONS

Camilo Ayala García

Assistant Professor

Faculty of Architecture & Design, Universidad de los Andes, Carrera 1 A No. 18A-70 Bogotá, Colombia.

✉ c.ayala954@uniandes.edu.co

ABSTRACT

As part of local availability of materials and processes research, this paper presents experimentation with methods to teach designers about materials. State of the art tools, technical and graphic literature and workshops are combined to place designers in an environment, which facilitates direct physical contact with materials. This allows students to understand the technical, mechanical and physical properties of materials, while easily comprehending their aesthetic and sensory attributes, and behaviour. In most cases, such experimentation leads to unconventional and ground-breaking solutions, which are different to what the industry commonly produces. Close interaction with materials and their in-depth understanding opens new directions, which inspire designers to create new product languages.

KEYWORDS: *Design methodologies; project based research; experimentation; materials and design.*

INTRODUCTION

Material Science, as broad as it is, can evolve only when the right material applications are set. For designers, most of the challenge lies in articulating the right material with the right form for desired use. This is usually achieved by understanding material properties, applied processes and typical applications. However, what happens when designers enter a more complex phase of interacting with materials, discovering unseen properties, crossing processes and discovering new applications, which then become an alternative *design process*? In the Department of Design at *Universidad de los Andes*, this question is used as a starting point for a materials lab and teaching resources research. During the research, we have encountered several obstacles, pursued some alternatives and derived some conclusions that have led the team to create a pilot course under the title *Design, Materials and Processes*. Over a year, this course has shown enormous creative potential for product development in the near future. Designers have combined state of the art literature & software, gained access to a broad worldwide source of material libraries, interacted with materials that are disconnected with associated processes and experimented with them to discover new languages for product design. In addition, the key factor has been material accessibility. Inaccessibility to material in terms of touch, feel, breakage, form or experimentation hinders a

designer's ability to innovate. Special attention is paid to local availability of materials.

Today, material libraries are considered key for designers, architects and engineers to develop projects. This enormously advanced field makes it easy to encounter several resources of material libraries, online as well as in the form of software [1]. Although in several cases they give specific information about a material, it is not sufficient for design purposes.

In the book *Materials and Design* (Ashby & Johnson 2002), this issue is dealt with, indicating that the mechanical and physical properties of a material are not the only things designers consider when it comes to its use for a particular purpose. It is important to explore other properties based more on perception and personality of materials. Attributes such as *Classic, Plain, Extravagant, Honest, Mature, Futuristic or Serious* among others are central to understanding a material for an ideal application [2]. Manzini (1989), one of the first authors to explore this subject stated in his book *La Materia dell'Invenzione* that a daily experience of objects around us is what determines certain qualities of materials. Stereotypes of common products are evoked through the materials used for their creation (stone walls, wood furniture, steel swords). The name of the material disappears and its personality becomes the fact, which we as humans recognize, giving the material cultural weight and dimension [3].

As designers, we must pay attention to both sides of the coin. Neither of them, when seen separately is sufficient to succeed in our goal of developing products that fulfil customer expectations and develop experiences around it.

In their book *Materiology*, Daniel Kula & Elodie Ternaux (2009) posted another feature that the research team has found interesting in the way materials are shown to designers. As the authors state, the intention of the book is to contribute to the dialogue between the creative and scientific fields for the good of the product [4]. In order to achieve this goal, we believe that the way materials are shown in the book is an interesting and rather novel idea. Materials are presented in their most honest and comprehensible form; either how they occur in nature or after they are processed prior to application. That may sound irrelevant, but we have encountered that most material data sheets have typical applications of materials indicated in them. This may limit designers to explore other uses or possibilities. As explained later on, this is a key feature in the developed methodology to teach students about materials. Not because common applications are wrong or inadequate (decades of effort and research from all over the world has gone into the conception of those applications), but certainly because the future designer has to understand materials based on their attributes and not their applications to innovate.

Budinski (2001) affirms that one of the first things that designers ask initially while considering the use of a specific material is whether the material is at hand [5]. Karana, Hekkert & Kandachar (2007) conducted a research in this field asking designers from In-house manufacturing companies and consultancy design studios, what sources for material selections are commonly used. As a conclusion, in several cases, designers create depending on what is available or can be found locally [6].

MFID *Materiales como fuente de inspiración para el Diseño* (Materials as a source to inspire design) is the name given to the research which advocates a methodology that encourages

students to interact with materials in a local context with top tools available. The methodology presented in this paper contains the tools to teach designers to achieve material comprehension to create a material proposal. This material proposal, if met with the desired standards, will be granted a place in a physical material library intended to maintain a source to inspire designers and encourage other institutions to network around new materials and possible applications based on experimentation.

METHOD

To encourage designers to learn about materials, the methodology developed in research and applied in the course included three main areas (Fig. 1) Processes, Materials and Design.

Processes Chapter

As mentioned before, processes are being taught separately as a unique area. Students learn about the four main families and their subsets that may give birth to a product: Forming, Cutting, Joining and Finishing. The book *Manufacturing Processes for Design Professionals* [7] is a key tool for this chapter. The book layout clearly presents the process involved with good graphics and relevant information about tooling and manufacturing costs. In addition, the author describes two elements of the layout that are fundamental to designers: *Design opportunities & Design considerations*. They are cues to keep in mind while understanding the processes; a strong element that designers may consider useful when interacting with a process. The second trigger of the learning process begins with the interaction of CES [8]; a remarkable tool used mainly in engineering that designers are unfamiliar with (Karana, Hekkert & Kandachar, 2007). It gives students a way to compare processes based on characteristics. The charts created with the software enlighten students with the novelty of what is presented.

Fig. 1. Design, Materials and Processes Course Layout.

Together with the CES process training phase comes an exercise called *What's in your world?* that aims to encourage students to look around and understand what their surroundings are made up of, based on what they have learned (Fig 2). On concluding the first third of the course and assuming that in many cases depending on the manufacturing processes involved, designers get little or no access to the manipulation stage of the process. In our research, we included a chef who had the specific task of reproducing almost all the industry processes used, with food in the kitchen as a factory. Although the full description of the workshop will not be explained in this paper, it is important to highlight that during that phase called *The basis of the processes* (Fig. 3), students understand how to physically transform matter into a project.

Materials Chapter

Entering into the second phase of the course where materials are the main focus, literature is switched based on the particulars and specifications of the matter. The course proceeds with a series of lectures based on the book *Materiology* [4] that,

as mentioned in the previous section, presents all the material families and subsets disconnected from an application. Alongside the lectures, key speakers are invited to talk about material properties. Engineers address mechanical, physical, chemical, thermal and optical properties, while designers talk about aesthetics and personality [2]. With technical and as described by Karana, Hekkert & Kandachar (2007) & (2010) *Intangible characteristics of Materials* or ICM [6], [9] in mind, students enter into a second CES interaction and a second exercise of *What's in our world?* focusing on observation of materials instead of processes.

For this phase, several products are examined through CES technical charts and common design tools [10] [11], which aim to show ICM attributes.

Design Chapter

For the final stage of the course, contact with materials and experimentation are key elements. For instance, if a designer is not capable of feeling, understanding and interacting with a

The image shows a screenshot of a software interface for a design exercise. At the top left, there is a header for 'Universidad de los Andes' and 'Facultad de Arquitectura y Diseño'. The main content area is titled 'PROCESSES' and features a large image of a Bionicle figure. To the right of the image is a text box with the following text: 'Muñeco de figuras Lego (Bionicle). Los procesos empleados para elaborar las piezas son: Inyección y perforado, debido a la complejidad de las piezas y a la funcionalidad que se les da al encajar de forma precisa para que no sean fáciles de desarmar, mantengan una posición estable, sean resistentes, pero a su vez, sean posibles de separar para lograr nuevas formas.' Below this text is a 'CES VALIDATION CHART' with the following sections: '1. Selection Data' (Database: CES EduPack 2012 Level 1 & 2), '2. Selection Stages' (Graph, Limit, Tree), '3. Results: 2 of 30 pass' (Show: Pass all Stages, Rank by: Alphabetical). The chart also shows a list of processes: 'Die casting' and 'Injection molding'. At the bottom of the interface, there is a photo credit: 'FOTO: David Rios, 2013'.

Fig. 2. *What's on your world?* Phase Chart.

Fig. 3. The basis of the processes Phase Chart.

material, no innovation through product can occur. The availability of materials in a local context is a key element for that interaction to take place. Although we encourage students to feel familiar with state of the art online resources such as Material Connexion [12], Materió [13] or Transmaterial [14], we have stated in the research that they don't provide all the required information a designer needs (at least if the designer has no access to their physical libraries). For this reason, students are encouraged to understand and put into practice all that they have learned about materials by experimenting with them. In order to contribute to a local material library being created at *Universidad de los Andes* as a pilot, this research is currently taking place.

Energy and Eco audits: Nowadays, product life cycles are important to guarantee efficiency and sustainability. An emphasis on the correct use of energy, embodied energy [15] and how this affects product development is gauged by the use of Eco

audit tool form CES. Although no specific product design project is scrutinised, it is crucial, when it comes to understanding materials, to deal with this particular subject.

MFID phase.

The experimentation phase starts with a selection based either on the designer's personal desire for a particular material or on its availability in the local market. It is important to underline that local availability of materials is maybe the most important factor considering that people interact with thousands of materials on a daily basis. These materials have splendid characteristics, which are taken for granted most of the time. One of the roles of a designer is to observe those materials and their interaction with people and translate them into a product language suitable for society and the environment [16].

Once the students select the material or a series of materials, they start researching possible processes involved in the experimentation to create new languages of product design. It is important to underline that the students have the liberty to decide whether they want to replicate an industry process to give shape to a particular product (this happens when students have a particular interest to replicate a product they like in order to understand capabilities of the material for further designs), or to cross processes in order to explore new combinations of *material-process* to explore new languages.

Once the path is chosen, the protocols for experimentation are set. Students must be sure that the experiment is feasible, that there is no potential risk for the student or for the location where the experiment is conducted. Engineers, scientists and technicians are deeply involved in this phase in order to guarantee no harm comes to anyone (Fig 4).

Also important in terms of success in experimentation with materials is the use of charts as guidelines. This is why CES

and literature [2] [3] [4] [7] come handy when developing the basic charts that will determine properties to consider either for materials or the processes involved.

Mood boards have been proven to be key visual and graphic support elements for designers, to elaborate the intention of a particular project [11]. At this moment, students are asked to develop boards that will express—in terms of ICM—what the material is going to suggest. This may be the target vision that will lead the experiment to pursue an intended goal. Without mood boards, the experiment will remain a mere interaction with a material and won't establish a dialogue between designer and material. Mood boards should be seen as a tool for transformation. They are not static. If the experiment with a material is starting to suggest attributes or behaviours, those may be included on the board later on.

With protocols, materials & processes charts and mood boards at hand, students begin with an experimentation process that will lead to the creation of a piece that can compete to be included in the local material library.

Universidad de los Andes Facultad de Arquitectura y Diseño profesor CAMILO AYALA G. curso DISEÑO, MATERIALES Y PROCESOS FICHA DE EJERCICIOS c.ayala@uniandes.edu.co DISE-3437					
DESIGN					
TASK	PLACE	TOOLS	MATERIALS	RISK	COUNTERACT
Cortes en madera	Cc - Taller Corcas	-Overol -Tapabocas -Gafas protectoras -Caladora -Máquina de corte laser	Retablos de madera	Riesgos de corte y heridas con la maquinaria	-Trabajar con los elementos de seguridad. -Personal del taller que realice una monitoría sobre el trabajo realizado y del buen uso de las máquinas necesarias.
Acabados en madera 1. Quemar 2. Congelar 3. Envejecer / desgastar 4. Pulir	Cc - Taller Corcas	-Overol -Tapabocas -Gafas protectoras -Guantes de nitrilo -Pistola de calor -Lijadora de mano -Gubias	Retablos de madera Químicos Oxidantes Sustancias para acabados Sustancias genericas (Cloro / Alcohol)	-Quemaduras en la piel por contacto con las sustancias adhesivas e irritación.	-Consejar las sustancias adhesivas en lugares abiertos debidamente marcadas. -Hacer un buen uso de los mismos evitando riesgos para otras personas. -Hacer uso de elementos de protección.
Cortes en cobre	Cc - Taller Corcas No - Taller Joyería	-Overol -Tapabocas -Gafas protectoras -Sierra de Joyería	Láminas de Cobre	Riesgos de raspaduras	-Hacer un buen uso de los mismos evitando riesgos para otras personas. -Hacer uso de los elementos de protección. -Marcar los elementos contenedores de las sustancias químicas.
Unión de cobre	Cc - Taller Corcas No - Taller Joyería	-Overol -Tapabocas -Gafas protectoras	Láminas de Cobre Soldadura Adhesivos de metal	-Quemaduras con soldadura. -Irritación de la piel al entrar en contacto.	-Hacer un buen uso de los mismos evitando riesgos para otras personas. -Hacer uso de los elementos de protección. -Marcar los elementos contenedores de las sustancias químicas.
Acabados en cobre 1. Quemar / Congelar 2. Abrasión 3. Envejecer / desgastar 4. Oxidar / Pintar 5. Estampar	Cc - Taller Corcas No - Taller Joyería	-Overol -Tapabocas -Gafas protectoras -Contenedores -Lijas -Pinceles -Láminadora	Láminas de Cobre Soldadura Químicos oxidantes Pintura Abrasivos	-Quemaduras en la piel por contacto con las sustancias adhesivas e irritación. -Aspiración de gases tóxicos	-Hacer un buen uso de los mismos evitando riesgos para otras personas. -Hacer uso de los elementos de protección. -Marcar los elementos contenedores de las sustancias químicas.

Fig. 4. Experimentation Protocols.

No experiment will be considered valid if a clear guide is not included. A format is provide to guarantee that the interaction with a material is fully replicable by others and to avoid what can be called a *stroke of good luck*. Crucial data like a map of the city where students can highlight the source of material (this will led to generation a big picture view of local availability of materials), a step by step photo instructions, quantity of material used, format available, dimensions, other materials required and tools involved complete the chart.

RESULTS

The delivery of the new experiment with a material begins with the process chart (Fig. 5).

D- *Location of the material*: Highlights on a city map where the material was found. Several entries are permitted because the student may have previously undertaken research to compare prices and technical sheets (if any).

- B- *Materials required*: Description of materials utilized to complete the experimentation. In some cases some materials, chemical components, or layering is required and this is described.
- C- *Tools*: List of the tools, machinery and supports used to complete the task. It has happened that students get access to a particular industry to fulfil their goal, so respective credits are mentioned.
- D- *Photo Recipe*: A step-by-step photo record of the experimentation to illustrate the process with a short description of each step.
- E- *Description*: Short description of the experiment and intention.
- F- *Footnotes*: Additional information needed to complete the experiment.
- G- *Key Shot*: Advertising style photography of the material created with basic principles of composition and set up.

Fig. 5. MFID Experimentation Process Chart.

H- Credits: Information for the material library catalogue: author, and institutional data.

3.1. Example 1: An experiment involving polyamide with two types of temperature & thermoforming process. (Fig. 6-7).

3.2. Example 2: An experiment deforming PMMA using focalized temperature (Fig. 8-9).

Students are invited to present their final result in an exhibition open to the public where the whole process that led to the obtention of the new material is presented. Poster size pictures of the material accompanied by a sort of book that includes the new material and the instructions to obtain it (Fig 10). There will be no success without previous observation and understanding of materials and processes.

POLIAMIDA / TERMOFORMADO

MATERIAL Poliamida 0,50 mm
CANT 240 metros

OTROS MATERIALES
Molde de madera
Lamina de mdf(3mm)
Polietileno

HERRAMIENTAS
Pistola de calor
Termoformadora

Este proceso permite generar una superficie porosa, irregular y rígida que al someterse a altas temperaturas recrea una nueva textura y un lenguaje visual. A su vez, el material que se genera puede ser sometido al proceso de termoformado que permite obtener la forma de un molde o superficie. Sin embargo, no se garantiza un termoformado detallado de la pieza otorgándole un nuevo aspecto y materialidad.

¿Dónde comprar los materiales en Bogotá?

MFID

Envolver la poliamida en una lamina de mdf de 25 x 25cm , cubriendo toda la superficie por ambas caras de la tapa. Realizar un doble nudo al final.

Quemar el material a una temperatura de 430 C con una pistola de calor, colocándola a una distancia de 5 cm de la superficie hasta obtener el quemado del material.

Esperar 4 minutos hasta que el material se enfríe totalmente a temperatura ambiente.

Desmoldar la lámina del material quemado, realizando cortes por los bordes de la pieza.

Cortar la pieza restante en dos mitades iguales para obtener dos láminas del mismo tamaño.

Tomar una de las placas del material obtenido y introducirla entre dos laminas de polietileno para empaques prensándola en el marco de la termoformadora.

Encender la termoformadora y esperar 10 min hasta que se caliente.

Calentar los materiales durante 3 min hasta que la capa del material de la parte inferior forma una burbuja hacia abajo.

Realizar el proceso de termoformado : cargar la bomba, traer el marco, subir el molde, e inmediatamente cerrar la bomba de vacío.

Dejar enfriar por 2 min aproximadamente, proporcionándole ventilación.

Desmoldar el molde de madera con cuidado ejerciendo un poco de fuerza en los bordes de la placa termoformada para evitar que el material se pueda deformar.

Si se desea, separar la capa de polietileno de la poliamida haciendo un leve corte en el extremo y despegando suavemente para que la superficie de poliamida no se quiebre ni se desgaste.

Fig. 6. MFID Experimentation Process Chart. Student: Mariana Chacón

FOTO 1 EXPERIMENTACIÓN (Material como lenguaje)

Fig. 7. MFID Key Shot. Student: Mariana Chacón

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Polimetacrilato / Quema

MATERIAL PMMA

CANT Láminas de min 3mm de espesor.

OTROS MATERIALES

Puede ser remplazado por láminas de (PS) de igual espesor.

HERRAMIENTAS

Pistola de calor
Pinzas

Por medio de este proceso es posible generar una nueva forma texturizado en las láminas de PMMA permitiendo que el material adquiera una estética y un lenguaje agresivo y poco común. Nunca antes trabajado el cual es posible manipular a partir de uso controlado de la aplicación de calor. Las piezas resultantes de este proceso son únicas.

(¿Dónde comprar Plástico en Bogotá?)

Fotografías: Maira Leguizamo

Aplicar calor constante por medio de una pistola de calor sobre la superficie de la lámina de PMMA hasta conseguir sobre la misma un texturizado poroso color mate.

Aplicar calor constante en el lado opuesto empezando desde los bordes de la pieza. Aplicar calor mientras sucede la transformación hasta lograr la forma deseada.

Fotografías: Maira Leguizamo

Finalmente al obtener la pieza deseada es importante dejar de aplicar calor a la pieza debido a que esto causa la pérdida del texturizado y la forma adquirida. Dejar enfriar.

Fig. 8. MFiD Experimentation Process Chart. Student: Maira Leguizamo

Fig. 9. MFiD Experimentation Sheet. Student: Maira Leguizamo

Fig. 10. MFiD Experimentation Book ready for the material library.

DISCUSSION

The iterative process of interacting with a material in a workshop or a lab proves that designers are capable of extracting new data from a material even if it is one of the most commonly used in the market. The experiment results in new perspectives of materials and inspires further applications.

Designers have the capability to reinterpret a material's language if the right pathway is set. There is no unique methodology or an exclusive pathway to reach that goal but the sum of different theories, research and tools is fundamental. The future of materials lies in how people interact with them, how those materials are perceived by a society and how they can transform and evolve at the same speed that humans do.

The course exhibitions have led to unexpected situations where for instance, engineering, art and architecture students are willing to take the course. It is remarkable to see how students from other departments get involved and excited to work with this methodology to unlock their creative pathways, thanks to materials.

One common reaction that occurs when people are invited to the exhibition is surprise accompanied with the expression suggesting that they didn't know that a particular material could look a particular way or behave otherwise.

Although this isn't new in the field of design because one can see material experiments and new product languages every year at fairs like *Salone del Mobile* in Milan [17], *London Design Festival* [18] or *La maison de objet* in Paris [19], it is important to imprint this art of methodologies on future designers, engineers, architects and artists. New technologies are evolving; for instance, FabLabs & 3d Printing are on the way to displace classic manufacturing processes and people are getting more access to industry, opening gates to customization and product experience [20]. If designers are aware of the potential they have in hand while interacting and experimenting with materials, a new industry will emerge sooner than we expected with more sustainability and efficiency in the process of transformation and creation of products of any kind.

Special attention to intellectual property also needs to be given. We are aware in the research that open sources and social networks are the way to a near future where sharing is more constructive than hiding knowledge about material, especially in the field of design. It is important to underline and develop a correct line of action whereby creators of the material receive due recognition and protection of their work with the right balance of sharing and collaboration with the industry. We are still working to complete this task.

CONCLUSIONS

Physical interaction is a desirable and necessary condition to accompany the design process to lead to innovation. Although this is a methodology developed for the early stages of design studies, it is important to apply it further for

professional development. If a designer with a clear pathway to experiment with materials gets the chance to enter a particular industry, he will be able to make substantial changes to its structure and goals. With the spread of that methodology, new product languages will hit the market in a sustainable long term fashion sooner than expected, in a world dominated by standardization and global boredom, where the same shapes and discourses are found in different typologies of products but at varying scales. The correct balance between the technical and perceived properties of a material will lead to new material interpretations and inspire more emotional and desirable applications.

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APPLYING SYSTEMIC DESIGN ON HUMAN PROCESSES

A FIRST APPROACH TO SUSTAINABLE ANTHROP-O-SYSTEMS

Daniela Restrepo Ortiz
Industrial Designer MSc. in Eco-design
Co-creator Life Jam – Design Network for Sustainable Humanity
✉ daniela.restrepo.ortiz@gmail.com
✉ lifejammers@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The following research seeks to understand how disciplines such as Systemic Design can be applied to human relations in order to establish the concepts of a new social phenomenon. Its purpose is to activate a new interdisciplinary culture, to create a network of knowledge, to outline a dialogue between the diverse disciplines that depend on each other to provide more sustainable solutions to the world's complex issues. This ongoing research seeks to analyze how the study of human dimensions from different areas can be used to design strategies that can socially innovate. The research itself represents a backup study to the development and design of integrated and systemic experiences. By merging design with psychological branches such as Logotherapy, we will provide an example of possible applications of the theory.

KEYWORDS: *Systemic Design, Logotherapy, Sustainability, and Anthrop-o-systems.*

INTRODUCTION

Designers continue to approach an object, a space or even a service, in an attempt to solve specific problems. What if a more integrated praxis of design and emotion is missing? Can the current design practices be integrated into other fields of action? Nowadays, society's most complex issues related to education, fair trade, sanitation, pollution, human rights, climate change and others, continue to grow (especially in developing countries). Design processes *can* constitute an integrative experience that leads to the resolution of such conflicts and the improvement of human conditions. Therefore, it becomes vital to understand where design is leading to and how it can serve to provoke real change.

SYSTEMIC DESIGN

The Politecnico di Torino (Italy) has recently proved that **Systemic Design** shows a new perspective towards more sustainable solutions. **Sustainability** is understood in this paper as the by-product of diverse strategies (social, economic, commercial, political, and others) that project the elements of a system in such a way that it becomes self-sufficient, with a

tendency to zero emissions. From that perspective, design practitioners have witnessed a drastic change in the role that design can now play in society. Italian designer and professor, Luigi Bistagnino projects sustainability from a productive, territorial and cultural viewpoint. He specifically describes this branch of design as follows:

“Systemic Design projects the relations between the components that generate a system (...) gives value to the *identity* and local resources producing development and welfare both for individuals and collectivities. The relationships between each component are generated through interaction to create balance and the result is the quality of the created system.” (Bistagnino, 2009)

Concepts such as *identity* and *human behavior* become essential in the analysis of the components that generate a system. Granting value to human beings and placing them at the center of the projects, not as the main and most important actor, but as one that is able to integrate the resources, cultural aspects and other elements of its environment, in order to connect and recover what is now being wasted.

Systemic Design has been suggested as a term for this emerging movement in design, also known as Systems Oriented Design or Whole Systems Design. Academies such as the Oslo School of Architecture and Design (Oslo, Norway) have been setting up periodic events and workshops involving students

Figure 1. Systemic Design (Bistagnino, 2009)

and teachers in the discussion of new strategies and tools regarding this topic. One of the most recent conclusions of these meetings was:

“What binds systems related theories and practices together with design approaches may be the desire to reintroduce systems approaches with design toward a more effective integrated praxis (...). This implies the reshaping and design of systems approaches and the related practices so that they are better integrated into design processes.” (Oslo School of Architecture & Design, 2013)

The transition from a linear thinking process to a systemic one has already been made not only by designers but by other professionals as well. Even though one of the fathers of system's theory is Ludwin von Bertalanfy, throughout history, characters involved in the study of human evolution have applied a more integral approach in their areas of study. Such is the case of **Urie Bronfenbrenner** in psychology and **Ezio Manzini** in the

fields of design and social innovation. Many other important authors have applied systemic thinking in the creation of commercial and economical strategies such as **Gunter Pauli** (seen in his theory on the Blue Economy), and in philosophical, ecological and spiritual fields such as **Ken Wilber** (which we will look at later on).

URIE BRONFENBRENNER AND THE ECOLOGICAL SYSTEMS THEORY

This American psychologist was known for developing the Ecological Systems Theory. Bronfenbrenner's theory was ecological for he added biological influences to his studies. He approached human development as a life-spent system from childhood to adulthood. The theory states that development reflects the influence of mini environmental systems. (Olson, 2007).

Figure 2. Interpretation of Eric Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory. There are five environmental systems: 1) Microsystems, 2) Mesosystems, 3) Exosystems, 4) Macrosystems and 5) Chronosystems. These systems are embedded into each other and get bigger as they branch out. They help to emphasize how important environmental factors are (Olson, 2007).

The Ecological System theory shows that it is important to understand the life styles of individuals and their development because it helps to explain human interaction and how people's lives and events are influenced by their surroundings. Bronfenbrenner's theory was applied in the area of education and in the analysis of childhood development, opening the path to new ways of connecting systemic thinking to the understanding of human behaviors.

FROM ECOLOGICAL VIEWPOINTS TO PRODUCTIVE PROCESSES

Furthermore, in business management, productive processes and within the industrial field, systemic approaches have been applied to design new methodologies. The **Product-service system (PSS)**, also known as a function-oriented business model, is a model that aims to provide sustainable consumption and production. A Product-Service System is created when a stakeholder (firm, enterprise, etc.) offers a mix of both products and services, in contrast to the traditional focus on products (Cooka, 2006).

Social sciences, business, design and technology gave birth to what is now known as Service Design. From these areas, several tools were taken to contribute to Industrial Design, which has seen the development and establishment of several methods and techniques over the years. This period has witnessed the birth of new tools (specific to the Service Design practice) that are able to reach a higher level of complexity and to communicate the immaterial aspects of a project such as time and experience (Tassi, 2009). The similarity between systems approach and Service Design lies within the actors' involvement in service creation, development and delivery, in terms of their roles and resources. Describing a system means identifying the main figures involved, becoming more deeply acquainted with the actors' features and the existing relations between them. It specifies their activities and aims to take part in the service process (Tassi, 2009). Therefore, the two approaches do not compete against each other; instead, they are meant to co-develop new creative structures especially to project social innovation programs.

EZIO MANZINI AND DESIS

The collaboration between systems approach and Service Design can be seen in DESIS (Design for Social Innovation towards Sustainability). This is a network of design labs and design-oriented organizations, actively involved in promoting and supporting sustainable change. Ezio Manzini, one of Italy's greatest social innovators and president of the DESIS network, established what could be the building blocks of a new way of doing design (and to conceive human relations). He invites designers to change their focus of observation in order to become interpreters of human phenomena. According to Manzini, users should not be seen as bearers of necessities but as bearers of capacities: designers are in charge of observing

society **when** and **where** new organizations that construct new ways of **being** or **doing** are born. These moments are the result of a creative moment that transforms into a valuable entrepreneurship initiative (Manzini, 2010).

FIRST APPROACH TO SUSTAINABLE ANTHROP-O-SYSTEMS

Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems theory and projects such as DESIS, clearly demonstrate that applying systemic theory to social, productive, economic, commercial and environmental processes *can* promote the creation of innovative solutions. Brand new ideas are waiting to be explored and now designers have a chance to project their creativity integrally.

So, what about those designers concerned with the development of new social practices that can lead to measurable impacts on communities? Manzini proves that if human relations could be interpreted not only as common and usual behaviors, but also as flows of information, transmission of messages, signals and more, designers could be approaching a new area of intervention in social innovation. Human systems or *Anthrop-o-systems* (as they will be referred to in the present paper) are made up of a series of elements that not only refer to an existing being, but also to a series of inputs and outputs that are constantly coming in and out of every individual. Such is the case of a community in which a group of individuals exchanges inputs and outputs. Nonetheless, a community is placed in a certain locality: a city, a country, a continent and so on. Truth is, there is more to the matter than meets the eye: philosopher Ken Wilber has studied the complexity of a part and a whole. One of Wilber's key concepts is to study and categorize items in terms of their nature as holons, a term derived from the writings of Arthur Koestler. He noticed that every entity and concept shares a dual role: both being autonomous, self-sufficient units (whole entity) unto themselves, and also a part of one (or more) other wholes (Koestler, 1967). An example of this is the way in which a cell in an organism is both a whole as a cell and at the same time a part of another whole, which is the organism. Everything from qualks, to matter, to energy, to ideas can be perceived in this way.

SYSTEMIC DESIGN AND ANTHROP-O-SYSTEMS

When analyzing the main tenants and the philosophy of Systemic Design from the perspective of Prof. Bistagnino (Politecnico di Torino), certain similarities regarding the subject of sustainable Anthrop-o-systems became evident. Each one of the following principles has an application in human relations as well. There are five main principles to design according to this systemic approach. Next to each one of them, a parallel with Anthrop-o-systems will be made.

1) A system's outputs and/or wastes have to be transformed into inputs and/or resources of another system. (Bistagnino, 2009)

This means that in order to develop sustainably, everything that comes in and out of a human being needs to be transformed into what comes in or out of another human being. Individuals need to be more aware of the fact that everything is entirely recyclable: not only their waste but also their experiences, their words and everything involved in their daily activities. From the material to the immaterial (from an object to an emotion).

2) A system has to be generated from inner and outer relationships that contribute to the system. (Bistagnino, 2009)

An Anthrop-o-system needs to be generated from the inner relationships of the individual as well as the outer relationships that surround him/her. The relationship between individuals and society should work in the same way, for individuals and societies are both holons within a bigger holon.

3) A system needs to be self-generated, meaning that it has to sustain from its automatic self-production, defining its own action and coevolving as a unit. (Bistagnino, 2009)

When coevolving as an automatic self-produced unit, an Anthrop-o-system is able to transform and impact its own community when relating collectively with other Anthrop-o-systems. This means that design practitioners have the challenging task of scaling-up human resources and all that this implies.

4) Acting locally: The local environment is fundamental because there has to be a valorization of human, material and cultural local resources that work to solve social, cultural and ethical problems (Bistagnino, 2009).

An Anthrop-o-system needs to take advantage of the closest resources at hand, meaning that it will not only rescue the identity and authenticity of what is local, but it will also generate a cultural statement through its interaction with the context. There is a need to focus on local specificities when working with Anthrop-o-systems rescuing not only fundamental aspects such as language, but also local expressions, folklore, cultural assets and more.

5) Human beings have to be at the center of the project, coevolving with other fluxes and connected with the system and local environment in a social, cultural and ethical manner. (Bistagnino, 2009)

Once again, it becomes evident that humans need to be placed at the center of the project itself. This means that human activity (including its material and immaterial processes) needs to be analyzed, decomposed and represented in fluxes that show interconnectedness and interdependence between each particular element.

What would an Anthrop-o-system look like according to these principles and applying systemic theories? In order to represent one of these systems, *Human Needs* and *Human-scale Development* established by Manfred Max-Neef were taken into account. They were chosen for this analysis because they are few, finite and classifiable as well as constant through all human cultures and across historical time periods. What changes over time and between cultures, are the strategies by which these needs are satisfied (Max-Neef, 1989).

Figure 3. Anthrop-o-system. The diagram was developed according to Max-Neef and his classification of the fundamental human needs: subsistence, protection, affection, understanding, participation, leisure, creation, identity and freedom. Needs are also defined according to the existential categories of being, having, doing and interacting. Every human activity is influenced by these dimensions.

An Anthrop-o-system could become a more widely-used tool if design practitioners interpret it not only as an element of any system but also as a holon (applying Wilber's concept): a whole system part of another system, in particular, if they are creating experiences that relate to social and emotional factors. The following diagram explains how Systemic Design was used for the planning of an After School Program. It was part of a tendering process in a project for public schools in Bogota (Colombia) that has not yet been approved.

The inner relations of this specific Anthrop-o-system are not only regulated within each individual, but the interaction between different stakeholders begins and starts to create a network of collaborative education. This means that the outputs of a stakeholder could become the input of another actor; the community in which the program is implemented becomes a local provider of resources as well as the receptor of those inputs. Even though the project has not been executed, the Systemic Design approach has contributed to create unique methodologies that can trigger a positive change and evolution of the education paradigm in Colombia.

The graphic representation of this project is similar to that which is used as a tool in Service Design: a blueprint. The **service blueprint** is a technique used for service innovation. Lynn Shostack, a bank executive, first described this technique in a 1984 Harvard Business Review. The blueprint shows processes within a company, divided into different components, which are separated by lines. The traditional blueprints (as used in disciplines like product design, architecture and

engineering) are instruments for building, standardizing, communicating, planning and sharing a project (Shostack, 1984). While analyzing how blueprints are used in Service Design, it becomes obvious that they give only a partial representation of how a service works: they provide a detailed visualization of the actions and processes, without looking at the motivational and emotional sides (Tassi, 2009).

INTERVENTION OF LOGOTHERAPY IN ANTHROP-O-SYSTEMS

In order to apply systemic theories in human matters, it becomes necessary to link this with other anthropological, sociological and especially psychological studies that have been performed. Logotherapy or Existential Analysis (LTEA), established by psychiatrist and neurologist Viktor Emil Frankl (1905-1997) in the 1930s, is an internationally acknowledged meaning-centered approach to psychotherapy. There is a fundamental element from Logotherapy that may be interpreted as a tool for providing sustainability to an Anthrop-o-system. This is the concept of **self-distancing** which gives human beings the capacity to distance themselves from their own heritage, conditioning or whatever else influences them to act in a particular way.

“According to LTEA humans are not fully subject to conditions but are basically free to decide and capable of taking their stance towards internal (psychological) and external (biological

Figure 4. Application of Systemic Design in the planning of an after-school program for public schools of Bogotá (Colombia).

and social) conditions. Freedom is here defined as the space to shape one's own life within the limits of the given possibilities.” (Batthyany, 2010)

Self-distancing implies the development of meta-cognitive skills: a learner's automatic awareness of their own knowledge and their ability to understand, control, and manipulate their own cognitive and emotional processes (Martínez, 2007). It means to be able to act differently to the direction in which the feelings manipulate an individual. That is, opposing what the person is feeling not to fight against those feelings, but to adapt to different perspectives. Therefore, self-distancing becomes the means through which an individual can actually relate to what surrounds him/her: a situation, a person, a feeling, or a message. It means that if self-distancing becomes a response to several stimuli, the inputs and outputs of an Anthrop-o-system *can* actually be controlled or measured by the individual that produces, transmits and receives them.

The following Figure shows the intervention of self-distancing in two specific activities: talking and listening. They are both satisfiers of the human need for participation from the interaction categories of being (Max-Neef, 1989). The communication skills of an individual unable to self-distance from his inner (and external) conditions are going to be limited. Nonetheless, the individual that is able to self-distance from what he hears (leaving aside his inner emotions, feelings, conditionings etc.) will be able to interact more efficiently.

The example makes clear that both spoken and heard messages become inputs and outputs within these two Anthrop-o-systems interacting in a conversation. The quality of both inputs and outputs, depends on the will of the subject to self-distance or not.

CONCLUSIONS

The world in which designers create these days is full of challenges that go beyond the regular design praxis. This task is not easy, as designers need to assume the role of *connectors* and “sponges” absorbent and permeable to all sorts of theories. The application of combinatory thinking is a requirement now, and design-oriented academies (as well as other educative institutions) need to provide such tools and knowledge.

Systems theory and most importantly Systemic Design can be used to project experiences that give rise to human beings' need to effectively connect and relate to others. This might be the key to solve many of our current global crises and, if used well, it could become a tool for communities to develop social strategies that can lead to real change and improvement of life conditions. It is evident that Anthrop-o-systems can have an important role in social innovation if understood and applied as a method to connect and communicate. Linking solutions to emotions that can be regulated by self-distancing *could* make a difference. The unique combination between Logotherapy and Anthrop-o-systems may guarantee an important and innovative progress in Systemic Design approaches.

Since Systemic Design gives us the chance to decompose the parts of a whole and, at the same time, merge these elements together in a web of knowledge, it represents a basic tool for social entrepreneurs and it should be used in the planning, development and implementation of any kind of program. We hope that, this will provide people with solutions that they can use to generate positive change. When we begin to understand social matters as whole and not as independent issues that cannot be solved collectively we *will* make a difference.

INTERACTING

Figure 5. Intervention of self-distancing in two activities: talking and listening.

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APPRAISAL ANALYSIS TO DESIGN PROCESS: A CASE STUDY ON EDUCATION

Jussana Ramos dos Santos
Universidade do Vale do Rio dos Sinos
✉ jussana.ramos@gmail.com
Leandro Miletto Tonetto
Universidade do Vale do Rio dos Sinos
Zooma – Consumer Experience
✉ ltonetto@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study examines the possibility, through an appraisals analysis, to qualify the experience of candidates for Master's degrees in order to reduce their anxiety when it comes to choosing these programs. Using a theoretical and methodological approach based on Appraisals Theory, in-depth interviews were conducted with 20 people (interested in applying to Master's in different areas), who reported anxiety when choosing their programs. Based on empirical results, it was possible to identify categories that were explored through the relationship with this theory. This analysis brought elements that have provided support for generating design guidelines in order to qualify the experiences of future Master's degree students.

KEYWORDS: *design process; design and emotion; emotional experience; appraisals theory; education.*

INTRODUCTION

The higher education scene in Brazil has shown an increasing number of graduate programs. This growth, however, brings challenges for higher education institutions that are seeking to attract students and secure a better position against their competitors. One way to attract new students is to qualify the applicant's experience. The *Design for Emotion* field, which is in focus of this short paper, aims to design products and services with the explicit intention of evoking or preventing certain emotions, so it can be easily related to the need for universities to qualify the experience of future students.

Among the different theoretical and methodological approaches to design for emotions, Appraisals Theory states that an emotion is the result of a person's appraisal regarding the potential effect of a stimulus on his or her welfare (Demir, Desmet and Hekkert, 2009). Based on this context, this study examines how it is possible, through an appraisal analysis, to qualify the experience of candidates for Master's degrees in order to prevent anxiety when it comes to choosing a course. It is important to emphasize that the focus is not career selection but the information seeking process, which is why the case study focuses on the stage of data collection with future candidates for a Master's program.

Although anxiety is an important point of this study, the authors did not intend to theoretically explore it in this short paper. Nevertheless, it is important to highlight that anxiety is commonly defined as an experience of fear and apprehension regarding an anticipation of potential danger, whether this is real or imagined (CASTILLO et al., 2000). The main reason for this choice (anxiety) is given by the results found in this study (explored in the "Results and Discussion" section). These results are based on the respondents' appraisals, which indicated anxiety as one of the common emotions evoked during the information seeking process for Master's courses. This analysis, therefore, resulted in an understanding that emotions and their causes can generate design stimuli that can help us to understand how to avoid anxiety among these students.

METHODS

The study had a qualitative approach, and fourteen in-depth interviews were conducted with people who applied for Master's courses. Participants were recruited during the application process for Master's courses at several Brazilian universities. They were accessed through these universities, which provided their e-mail addresses.

The authors contacted seventy-eight students who were in the information seeking process, in an estimated period of 30 days prior to the formalization of program enrolment. Twenty people answered the e-mails and were then sent a second e-mail, including a list of emotions as stimulus (Scherer, 2005). They were asked to indicate which of those emotions were experienced during the information seeking process. Since anxiety was mentioned by all participants, the authors have focused on conducting in-depth interviews only with those who did report it. Fourteen applicants participated in this stage.

A script to be used for data collection was adapted from Demir et al. (2009) considering issues related to the interaction of the users with services (not products). Data collection included the following steps:

- a) The participants received a word list of emotions based on Scherer's list (2005) and they selected three emotions. To raise awareness and familiarize themselves with the process of reporting their emotions, participants were asked to report experiences related to three emotions referred by them.
- b) An in-depth interview was conducted, focusing on the anxiety reported during the information seeking process of applying to a Master's course.
- c) The script for in-depth interviews followed the componential model of appraisals, which included seven questions to reflect the essence of the seven appraisal components (Demir et al., 2009): (1) During the information seeking process, did you achieve your goals? (Motive Consistency), (2) How enjoyable was this process? (Intrinsic pleasure), (3) How do you compare this process with others that you experienced in searching for information on other courses

and/or universities? (Standards conformance), (4) How does the information you found match (or not) your expectations? (Expectation confirmation), (5) How sure were you that the information you found is all you needed to know in terms of the future about these courses? (Certainty), (6) Whom, what event or what situation is responsible for potential hardships encountered in the process? (Agency), (7) How did you manage (or not) to deal with such adversity? (Coping potential). The aim of this script was to identify possible causes for anxiety (appraisals).

The average length of the interviews was 30 minutes. They were tape recorded for further scrutiny and Content Analysis. The data analysis was performed following the categorical analysis (Bardin, 1995), reorganizing the text by units. The process is defined by Moraes (1999) as categorization, since data were grouped according to what is common among them. After structuring results, it was possible to relate the categories (results) with the seven appraisal components (Demir et al., 2009). The results are presented in the next section.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows results at two levels: (a) the first two columns indicate the categories and subcategories, respectively, indicating the essence of the contents verbalized by respondents, but not related to any theoretical elements, (b) the other columns show the relationships between empirical results and theoretical components of appraisals. The words highlighted in red show the negative reviews provided by participants, in which they mention anxiety in their experience. The words highlighted in blue show the positive reviews.

	CATEGORIES AND SUBCATEGORIES	MOTIVE CONSISTENCY	INTRINSIC PLEASURE	EXPECTATIONS CONFIRMATION	AGENCY	STANDARDS CONFORMANCE	CERTAINTY	COPING POTENCIAL
INFORMATION	Unknown information	Inconsistent	---	Disconfirmed	Own candidate	---	Uncertainty	Low
	Level of clarity/ Lack of information	Inconsistent	---	Disconfirmed	Information sender	---	Uncertainty	Low
PROFESSIONAL RESOURCES	Website	Inconsistent	---	Disconfirmed	Information sender	Not Conformance	Uncertainty	Low
	Secretary attendance	Consistent	---	Confirmed	Information sender	Not Conformance	Certainty	High
	Professor attendance	Consistent	---	Confirmed	Information sender	Not Conformance	Certainty	High
	E-mail and phone attendance	Consistent	---	Confirmed	Information sender	Conformance	Certainty	High
NON-PROFESSIONAL RESOURCES	Own resources	Inconsistent	---	Expectation break down	Own candidate	---	Uncertainty	Low
	University location	Inconsistent	---	Disconfirmed	The university	Conformance	Uncertainty	Low
	Contact other people	Consistent	---	Confirmed	Reference people	---	Certainty	High

Table 1. Relation of Categories x Appraisals Components

Source: Authors (2013)

The “information” category was divided into two subcategories. First, unknown information was related to the real goals of a Master's degree, which should, according to the respondents, be demystified and better explained by higher education institutions offering courses at that level. The participants addressed this point by referencing the fact that they had no knowledge of what a Master's degree level can offer or ignorance in terms of what will occur after completion of the course. Second, lack of information is related to the understanding of what is offered by a Master's program. This subcategory was created according to the testimony of respondents who expressed anxiety for not understanding the information provided or demanded more complete information. In other words, the knowledge exists, but there is no confirmation of that. Consequently, anxiety was related to inconsistent reasons, not confirming expectations, various agencies, uncertainties and low coping potential.

The “professional resources” category involves people and sources of information that interested parties have sought in an attempt to answer their questions. These are organized into four subcategories. First, the information seeking process through the university website, is related to inconsistent reasons, expectation disconfirmation, agency (information sender), non-confirmation of standards, uncertainty and low coping potential. The second and third subcategories are related to each other in the sense that they represent face-to-face forms of interaction between applicants and university representatives. The fourth subcategory is related to email and telephone interaction of secretarial staff. The relationship of these three subcategories with the appraisal components showed that anxiety can be prevented through consistent motives, confirmation of expectations, certainties and high coping potential. However, for standards conformance, we observed reduced anxiety only through non-personal interaction, unlike the subcategories of the secretarial staff and professor attendance, in which there was anxiety related to non-compliant standards.

The “non-professional resources” category involves other information channels and/or forms through which stakeholders seek information to deal with situations that could generate negative emotions during the application process. This category is organized into three subcategories: own resources of applicants to deal with problems, the location of the university, and relationship and contact with other people.

In the “own resources” sub-category, one can say that each individual creates his or her own way to deal with the anxiety evoked by the process of looking for information and deciding. Negative results may arise if the person, after feeling anxious, decides not to look for information. Also, negative results may arise if the person does not look for information through the other channels, like those mentioned above. Thus, uncertainty and anxiety may develop substantially if the applicant does not know how to deal with such issues. Some participants mentioned the “location of university” as a cause of anxiety, even though it is not considered a resource that is managed by applicants during the information seeking process. Relating these two sub-components with the appraisals, we can see

that the triggers for anxiety can be inconsistent, no confirmation and break-down of expectations, agencies (the applicant and the university become responsible), uncertainties and low potential for coping.

The last subcategory, “relations and contact with other people” is related to the personal contacts that applicants have and use in order to deal with anxiety. These people play an important role because they use words of encouragement and help to clarify what a Master's course means and implies for the applicant's life. In this case, this subcategory shows that anxiety can be reduced if facing a consistent motive, confirming expectations, agency (who are people who serve as reference for applicants), certainty and a high coping potential.

CONCLUSION

The results provide insights for future design processes. According to Desmet and Hekkert (2009), understanding the emotions of users resulting from the interaction with a product or service can help the designer visualize, in advance, possible ways to avoid negative outcomes.

In this case, it was necessary, in addition to understanding the role of anxiety in this process, to comprehend the appraisals that lead to it. Exploring these causes, based on the evaluation components of Appraisal Theory, provides a better understanding of cause-effect relationships (design-anxiety), highlighting tangible elements to support the design process. Such comprehension, therefore, is important for discussion and understanding of ways that may serve as stimuli to designers when it comes to developing services.

Results from Table 1 showed that design for emotion, applied in the context of higher education services, has the potential to develop interventions that may reduce the anxiety experienced in the information seeking process of Master's courses. The following design inputs are provided:

- a) Regarding the level of clarity and lack of information about courses, it is important to design consistent ways of providing information, considering the user's actual doubts and level of comprehension.
- b) Designing websites that facilitate access to clearer information and that may allow that may allow for controlled changed to be made by the users, following their language and understanding of the intended courses.
- c) The designer may use different elements of assistance from the secretarial staff and professors explored by users and so design artefacts that exceed the desired pattern and reduce anxiety.
- d) The location of the university and applicants' own resources are elements that are not easily controlled by designers. However, professionals can design methods that contribute to increasing applicants' awareness of universities' predetermined rules in order to cope with the anxiety caused by this situation.

e) The category involving people that serve as a reference showed that they contribute positively to the information seeking process. In this case, it is clear that not all causes of anxiety in choosing a course are easily controllable by design, since it may be difficult to manage these people serving as reference.

Thus, future studies could help develop projects based on the aforementioned guidelines, which have the potential to reduce the anxiety of prospective students who want to apply for a Master's degree.

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MOVEMENT AND EXPERIENCES IN CONSTRUCTED SPACES

A DESCRIPTION OF SPATIAL EXPERIENCES, BASED ON MOVEMENT

Liselotte Vroman, Thierry Lagrange
 KU Leuven Faculty of Architecture, Luca School of Arts
 ✉ liselotte.vroman@kuleuven.be, thierry.lagrange@kuleuven.be

ABSTRACT

The present paper reflects an on-going research project, consisting of practice-based experiments examining movement in relation to spatial situations. Specific attention is paid to the way movement relates to emotion and experience.

In an earlier phase of this research project, it was established that two-dimensional alterations to a given space induce changes in spatial experience, which are reflected in the way a person moves in this space.

In this phase, the influence of three-dimensional spatial interventions is examined, with a particular focus on the movements made by the various participants. Through observation, questioning and LMA (Laban Movement Analysis), we attempted to reach a fundamental understanding of the relationship between humans and space.

Based on these observations, some initial reflections are formulated on the relationship between space, movement, emotion and experience. Also, with this procedure, the proposed method can be explored and fine-tuned.

KEYWORDS: *movement, design, space, emotion, experience*

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this study is to examine the effects a space and alterations to a familiar space may have on the feelings and experiences of the individuals making use of these spaces. As architects/designers, we start by focusing on the movements of the users of spaces. It seems viable, from this point of view, to clarify and attempt to understand the relation between man and his surrounding space by observing the way he moves his body in a given space.

The way we observe, register and record these dynamics and the way we design the spaces are derived from our architectural context.

This paper reports on the initial phase of this research process, for which the main objective was to delineate the research context and determine our research options. In a previous study - a series of experiments in which a subject's movements were observed and recorded as a two-dimensional pattern - we established that observing and recording movement (by means of a range of graphic techniques, for instance one that is based

on MOCAP) provides the observer with graphic records of the experience of the space (Vroman et al. 2011). Building on this earlier research, the present series of experiments will see the introduction of three-dimensional objects into the space. Also, the space in which the experiments will take place is to be closely examined and clearly defined. At the present stage of the research, no particular point of view has been adopted regarding the spatial design. An open perspective, which leaves open various possibilities, is our model of preference. Since we have chosen to take multiple aspects into account, at this stage the approach adopted by Camurri (Camurri et al., 2003) and Van Dyck (Van Dyck et al., 2013) cannot be applied in this case. Instead, a matrix (Figure 1) was developed in which a series of configurations were positioned in relation with the space that is to be examined. This matrix will, in this initial phase, function as a mapping tool, in order to ensure that the experiments we have executed can be placed within this artificially created context. In the matrix, we discriminate between a spatial setting on the one hand and the space in which the experiment takes place on the other hand. This results in a series of potential configurations, which may become

part of the research subject. The highlights mark those cells that have already been the object of experiments at this stage.

METHOD

The method consists of a series of exploratory, open experiments, based on a reiteration of previous experiment findings (Vroman et al., 2012). Because of the nature of experiments of this kind, the focus is on the process as well as on the results. "The artistic practice itself is an essential component of both

the research process and the research results" (Borgdorff, 2010, p. 51). The artistic practice Borgdorff mentions here refers to our experimental approach as architects-designers, as well as to the participants in the improvisation sessions. It is our intention to start a process of alternating action and reflection, which will continue through all ensuing stages (Lagrange, 2013, p. 81-91). All experiments will be captured by means of camera recordings and documented with analyses of the recording and verbal reflections on the experiments. At a later stage, the results are linked to the reflections issuing from the experiments and surveys.

ONE PERSON								
TWO OR MORE PERSONS	SINGLE 2D LINE DRAWING	SINGLE 3D OBJECT (CFR. LINE DRAWING)	MULTIPLE 2D LINE DRAWING	MULTIPLE 3D OBJECT (CFR. LINE DRAWING)	WIDE/ UNLIMITED SPACE	LIMITED SQUARED SPACE	LIMITED RECTANGULAR SPACE	LIMITED CIRCULAR SPACE
SINGLE 2D LINE DRAWING	SINGLE 2D LINE DRAWING	SINGLE 2D LINE DRAWING + SINGLE 3D OBJECT	SINGLE 2D LINE DRAWING + MULTIPLE 2D LINE DRAWING	SINGLE 2D LINE DRAWING + MULTIPLE 3D OBJECT	SINGLE 2D LINE DRAWING + WIDE/ UNLIMITED SPACE	SINGLE 2D LINE DRAWING + LIMITED SQUARED SPACE	SINGLE 2D LINE DRAWING + LIMITED RECTANGULAR SPACE	SINGLE 2D LINE DRAWING + LIMITED CIRCULAR SPACE
SINGLE 3D OBJECT (CFR. LINE DRAWING)	SINGLE 3D OBJECT + SINGLE 2D LINE DRAWING	SINGLE 3D OBJECT (CFR. LINE DRAWING)	SINGLE 3D OBJECT + MULTIPLE 2D LINE DRAWING	SINGLE 3D OBJECT + MULTIPLE 3D OBJECT	SINGLE 3D OBJECT + WIDE/ UNLIMITED SPACE	SINGLE 3D OBJECT + LIMITED SQUARED SPACE	SINGLE 3D OBJECT + LIMITED RECTANGULAR SPACE	SINGLE 3D OBJECT + LIMITED CIRCULAR SPACE
MULTIPLE 2D LINE DRAWING	MULTIPLE 2D LINE DRAWING + SINGLE 2D LINE DRAWING	MULTIPLE 2D LINE DRAWING + SINGLE 3D OBJECT	MULTIPLE 2D LINE DRAWING	MULTIPLE 2D LINE DRAWING + MULTIPLE 3D OBJECT	MULTIPLE 2D LINE DRAWING + WIDE/ UNLIMITED SPACE	MULTIPLE 2D LINE DRAWING + LIMITED SQUARED SPACE	MULTIPLE 2D LINE DRAWING + LIMITED RECTANGULAR SPACE	MULTIPLE 2D LINE DRAWING + LIMITED CIRCULAR SPACE
MULTIPLE 3D OBJECT (CFR. LINE DRAWING)	MULTIPLE 3D OBJECT + SINGLE 2D LINE DRAWING	MULTIPLE 3D OBJECT + SINGLE 3D OBJECT	MULTIPLE 3D OBJECT + MULTIPLE 2D LINE DRAWING	MULTIPLE 3D OBJECT (CFR. LINE DRAWING)	MULTIPLE 3D OBJECT + WIDE/ UNLIMITED SPACE	MULTIPLE 3D OBJECT + LIMITED SQUARED SPACE	MULTIPLE 3D OBJECT + LIMITED RECTANGULAR SPACE	MULTIPLE 3D OBJECT + LIMITED CIRCULAR SPACE
					WIDE/ UNLIMITED SPACE	WIDE/ UNLIMITED SPACE + LIMITED SQUARED SPACE	WIDE/ UNLIMITED SPACE + LIMITED RECTANGULAR SPACE	WIDE/ UNLIMITED SPACE + LIMITED CIRCULAR SPACE
WIDE/ UNLIMITED SPACE	WIDE/ UNLIMITED SPACE + SINGLE 2D LINE DRAWING	WIDE/ UNLIMITED SPACE + SINGLE 3D OBJECT	WIDE/ UNLIMITED SPACE + MULTIPLE 2D LINE DRAWING	WIDE/ UNLIMITED SPACE + MULTIPLE 3D OBJECT	WIDE/ UNLIMITED SPACE	WIDE/ UNLIMITED SPACE + LIMITED SQUARED SPACE	WIDE/ UNLIMITED SPACE + LIMITED RECTANGULAR SPACE	WIDE/ UNLIMITED SPACE + LIMITED CIRCULAR SPACE
						LIMITED SQUARED SPACE	LIMITED SQUARED SPACE + LIMITED RECTANGULAR SPACE	LIMITED SQUARED SPACE + LIMITED CIRCULAR SPACE
LIMITED SQUARED SPACE	LIMITED SQUARED SPACE + SINGLE 2D LINE DRAWING	LIMITED SQUARED SPACE + SINGLE 3D OBJECT	LIMITED SQUARED SPACE + MULTIPLE 2D LINE DRAWING	LIMITED SQUARED SPACE + MULTIPLE 3D OBJECT	LIMITED SQUARED SPACE + WIDE/ UNLIMITED SPACE	LIMITED SQUARED SPACE	LIMITED SQUARED SPACE + LIMITED RECTANGULAR SPACE	LIMITED SQUARED SPACE + LIMITED CIRCULAR SPACE
						LIMITED RECTANGULAR SPACE	LIMITED RECTANGULAR SPACE	LIMITED RECTANGULAR SPACE + LIMITED CIRCULAR SPACE
LIMITED RECTANGULAR SPACE	LIMITED RECTANGULAR SPACE + SINGLE 2D LINE DRAWING	LIMITED RECTANGULAR SPACE + SINGLE 3D OBJECT	LIMITED RECTANGULAR SPACE + MULTIPLE 2D LINE DRAWING	LIMITED RECTANGULAR SPACE + MULTIPLE 3D OBJECT	LIMITED RECTANGULAR SPACE + WIDE/ UNLIMITED SPACE	LIMITED RECTANGULAR SPACE + LIMITED SQUARED SPACE	LIMITED RECTANGULAR SPACE	LIMITED RECTANGULAR SPACE + LIMITED CIRCULAR SPACE
						LIMITED CIRCULAR SPACE	LIMITED CIRCULAR SPACE + LIMITED SQUARED SPACE	LIMITED CIRCULAR SPACE
LIMITED CIRCULAR SPACE	LIMITED CIRCULAR SPACE + SINGLE 2D LINE DRAWING	LIMITED CIRCULAR SPACE + SINGLE 3D OBJECT	LIMITED CIRCULAR SPACE + MULTIPLE 2D LINE DRAWING	LIMITED CIRCULAR SPACE + MULTIPLE 3D OBJECT	LIMITED CIRCULAR SPACE + WIDE/ UNLIMITED SPACE	LIMITED CIRCULAR SPACE + LIMITED SQUARED SPACE	LIMITED CIRCULAR SPACE + LIMITED RECTANGULAR SPACE	LIMITED CIRCULAR SPACE

Figure 1. Matrix: series of configurations

The movements will be analysed using LMA (Laban Movement Analysis), a system that includes five categories of elements (body, space, shape, effort, and relationship) to observe and describes all forms of bodily motion (Chen et al., 2011). Within the present research study, there will be a particular focus on the "space" component, which comprises the various concepts that describe pathways of human motion within a frame of reference - "carving shapes in space" (Bartenieff & Lewis, 1980). Kinesphere and dynamosphere are key notions here. The kinesphere is that part of space which can be reached with the extremities. The zones of the kinesphere become apparent and are felt the moment when they are touched by the moving body. (Laban, 1966, p. 29). The space in which our dynamic actions take place may be called 'dynamosphere' (Laban, 1966, p. 30).

As Laban states: "A definite movement with a definite trace form is always connected with inner happenings such as feelings, reflections, determinations of the will, and other emotional impulses" (Laban, 1966, p. 88). Besides describing movement in relation to space, we will also endeavour to comprehend the emotion of the subject moving through the space by analysing his movements. LMA will be used as a technique to clarify the observed movements as part of a personal experience. At a later stage, this should feed the discourse on the relationship between movement, emotion, experience and space.

The fieldwork, as described below, consisted of two experimental phases. In the first phase, a series of open-ended, explorative experiments was conducted in an artistic learning environment, by way of an introduction of the research question. Students from various artistic disciplines were involved. The purpose of these first experiments was to build an initial conceptual framework with regard to this space, stemming from the students' reflection. It also served as a test case to check the effects of various spatial configurations. These configurations were an initial attempt to develop a specific spatial design. Each one represents one initial specific insertion of data in one cell of a display matrix.

FIELDWORK

The experiment consisted of eight four-hour sessions, in which students (usually a group of eight 20 to 24 year old males and females) were introduced to the concept of 'spatial awareness'. During these sessions, different spatial constellations were created onstage. Students were asked to go onstage and improvise for about twenty minutes. Their improvisations were supposed to be a reaction to impulses, issuing from either the performer himself, or his fellow-performers, or the space in which he evolved. In this instance, 'fellow-performers' are not only other people who are also onstage, but also elements of the space in which he or she performs. Each session was followed by a series of initial reflections on their experience of the space and the extent to which it had been different from their experience of the previous session. These reflections on their experiences and on the methods are what turns their ex-

periences into explicit experiences and should lead to a better understanding of the phenomenon of experience. The challenge is not so much finding a definition of 'experience' but rather approaching it in such a way as to be able to understand where it occurs and can be observed.

These sessions clearly showed how personal the movements made by the students onstage really are: each of the students brings his individual perspective and background to the task, and this was clear from their physical performance. Yet it was still possible to establish a pattern: the students' movements altered according to the various spatial configurations.

During our analysis of the movements, special attention was paid to the relationship between movements and the constellations in which they originated. As it is not possible to describe the movement sequences exhaustively, we focused on a specific number of them. We also tracked the "pathways" through the space and how these differed depending on the spatial constellations.

We were able to establish that when a 1,5 x 1,5 x 0,5 m cube was positioned centre stage (Figure 2) subjects chose mainly linear trajectories. The students kept their limbs close to their bodies. They moved mainly forward and downwards, and at relatively slow speeds. In the constellation where several cubes were disposed randomly on the stage (Figure 3), the trajectories meandered alongside the cubes. The students tended to favour closed trajectories, which led back to their starting point. The succession of transformations in the movement picks up speed and within the kinesphere several final frontiers were pushed.

Students described their spatial experiences with these two configurations as quite divergent. The configuration featuring a cube in the centre of the space was described as a "surface with a platform in the centre that exerts a strong attraction." The configuration featuring a number of cubes placed in the space at random, on the other hand, was described as "dynamic, relatively open, obstructive...."

As this phase was intended as an initial test case, a number of widely diverging configurations were put to the test, as seen in the display matrix. So, initially we do not start from the premise that there is a clear link between the space and the experience of this space. But from the students' reactions, we may surmise that this kind of experiment can contribute to the spatial awareness that arises from what they are feeling. From the sessions that took place in various configurations, it also became clear that the description of the students' onstage movements closely resembles their reflection on their experience of this space. With Damasio in mind, we know how emotions are related to feelings and the awareness (Damasio, 2001). An initial—provisional—conclusion might be that these movements, which are the result of a series of improvisations, are strongly related to forms of emotion. All observations, graphic expressions and debriefings point toward the possibility of experiences changing in relation to changing spatial setups. These experiences have an impact on body movements.

— KINESPHERE
— DYNAMOSPHERE

Figure 2. Cube positioned centre stage

Figure 3. Several cubes positioned randomly on stage

We should imagine our body movements as complex constellations in which emotions play a crucial role.

Besides this, the experiment allowed us to create a first draft of a conceptual framework for the experience of space. We retained the following notions: "dynamic, chaotic, circular, splintered, random, open, closed, variable and static." From these, "closed" and "open" were picked as elementary contrasting concepts, to be examined in the next experiment.

In the second phase, the configurations and the space in which the experiments were set up were scrutinised in more detail. We also had a closer look at the meaning of "open" and "closed" and how these notions come to the fore in the analyses of movement. One student, who had taken part in the previous phase of the experiment, participated in this session.

In this phase, the student was given three well-defined tasks. She was told to walk around, run and improvise freely, each

time for five minutes, within each of the configurations. The purpose of the experiment was to establish whether the impact of the spatial configuration would also manifest itself during the course of these three tasks. Both the tasks and the spatial configurations were fine-tuned. As a result, the various configurations could be more easily compared during this phase. During the reflection session, the student was asked whether space felt more “open-ended” or “closed.”

In the first instance, the space featured no configuration at all (Figure 4). The trajectories were squiggly and went in all directions. Within the kinesphere, movements were registered in the various levels and the final frontiers were reached. The student experienced this configuration as “open”, though she also indicated that the delineation of the space by the surrounding cameras limited her freedom of movement somewhat. In the configuration featuring a cube placed upright in the space

Figure 4. No configuration

Figure 5. Cube placed upright in the space

the space (Figure 5), the trajectories she chose while walking or running were mainly closed ones, as she regularly returned to the starting point. The cube acts as a landmark in this space, and also as a direction sign. The dynamosphere indicates the direction and the dynamic of the pathways that will be followed. It shows that movements in this setting are more rectilinear when a cube is placed in the room. We have also observed that whenever the cube was placed in the room, movement occurred more frequently in the lower area of the kinesphere. This might explain why the student had previously experienced this setup as closed.

We may conclude that modifications applied to a space have a distinct influence on how the space is experienced, but also on the way we move around in that space. We also established that the surrounding space (in this case the limited space comprising the camera field of vision) to a certain degree helps to define the experience of the configuration. For this reason, it is important to test the same configurations in a different “delimited space” in order to be able to evaluate its influence.

CONCLUSION AND FURTHER WORK

This first series of experiments has allowed us to formulate a tentative conceptual framework regarding the experience of a space. This enables us in a first instance to continue our research into the meaning in these notions and just how they are connected to a specific spatial experience.

The present research project is investigating the relationship between movement, emotion, experience and space. In this paper, we develop an approach focusing on the movement of a person, and thus the space this movement embodies. We observed how, depending on the spatial constellation, movement, emotion and, as a consequence, experiences, changed significantly. The present research allows us to reflect on the impact of space on emotion by closely observing this movement.

To date, these initial findings are only based on visual analyses of the filmed material and on verbal reflection. In future, we intend to focus on the development of a method based on the basic principles of LMA, to present a graphic image of movement in relation to spaces (comparable to previous research, Vroman et al., 2011), in order to be able to verify the first findings and to communicate them more clearly.

Both experimental phases constitute no more than an initial case study. Its degree of reproducibility still needs to be established. To this end, additional experimentation with different subjects is required. We will need to focus specifically on the description of the spatial constellations, the development of a well-considered conceptual framework to demonstrate the link between movement, emotion, experience and space.

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ARE YOU GOING TO WEAR YOUR WEARABLE FOR LIFE? DESIGNING FOR LONG-TERM SOCIAL HEALTH

Shin Sano, Sarah Rosenbach, Claudia Strenger

Institute for Creative Integration, San Francisco, CA, U.S.A.

✉ ssano@creative-integration.com, srosenbach@creative-integration.com, cstrenger@creative-integration.com

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a Model from which to develop design principles for products and services that promote long-term positive health and wellbeing. This Independency Model (IM) attempts to explain users' varying levels of dependent behavior and ways they can change that behavior. As a journey toward self-reliance, these behaviors represent failures in sustainable change partly due to short-term thinking, loss of impulse control or lack of positive feedback. Design principles for products and services should differ with each profile in order to best help people evolve to tech independence. While persuasive technologies, such as wearable activity trackers, aim to help people induce and adhere to healthy behaviors by tracking their status, creating awareness and giving action plans, they do not necessarily offer any "exit" strategies. This new model encourages products and services to be designed for people to "graduate" from the profile that is dependent on technologies, and internalize such independent healthy habits as their own.

KEY WORDS: *Persuasive technology, human behavior change, wearable devices, technology independence, internalized behavior.*

INTRODUCTION

There are a variety of wearable activity trackers that are designed with persuasive technologies, attempting to modify people's health-related behaviors, such as exercise, posture, heart rate, sleep patterns, emotional health and nutrition. These devices aim to promote healthy behaviors by providing constant reminders, encouragements and status awareness. However, many people disengage and/or discontinue the use of those devices and withdraw from healthy habits. Ledger et.al. (2014) suggest that more than half of U.S. consumers who have owned a modern activity tracker no longer use it. A third of U.S. consumers who have owned these devices stopped using them within six months of receiving them [1]. Although there is little evidence available to assess how their behavior has changed after they stop using such devices, most of them have likely relapsed into the state they were in prior to owning the devices.

There are, however, a number of studies showing enhanced utilization because of built-in feedback triggered by behavior patterns. Pina et. al. (2012) developed Fitbit +, that detects when people have been inactive in their work environment

for a long time and then prompts them to take a short break from their desks [2]. While there are several other systems that offer the same type of reminder function, such systems often propose cues at inconvenient times [2], cause cost or annoyance and fall into subsequent non utilization. BJ Fogg (2009) introduced the FBM model which suggests that for a person to perform a target behavior, he or she must (1) be sufficiently motivated, (2) have the ability to perform the behavior, and (3) be triggered to perform the behavior [3]. This model provides a solid theoretical and methodological foundation for designers of persuasive experiences to design artifacts that effectively trigger target behaviors.

However, the system design does not incorporate a pattern of exiting device usage and internalizing healthier behaviors on the consumer's own volition.

This paper introduces the Independency Model (IM), a conceptual model that classifies four different user profiles based on two factors; self-regulation capability and source of self-validation reference. This model identifies what types of supports are needed for people who fall into each quadrant in order to migrate into the independent profile. These user profiles can be viewed as phases that users go through,

where the activity tracking device plays an effective role, but only as a waypoint towards an independent healthy lifestyle without relying on tracking devices.

DISCUSSIONS

The Independency Model (IM)

The IM can be described as a 2x2 matrix [Figure 1] with an attribute of self-regulation capability; High or Low and an attribute of source of self-validation reference; Internal or External. On the vertical axis, self-regulation refers to a person's capacity for altering their behavior. It greatly increases the flexibility and adaptability of human behavior, enabling people to adjust their actions to a remarkably broad range of social and situational demands. It has four subcomponents: standard, monitoring, willpower and motivation to meet the standard (Baumeister et.al. 2007) [4]. High on the axis means high self-regulation capabilities, whereas low on the axis indicates a low capability of altering behavior. In the context of health related behavior, people categorized in the upper two quadrants are relatively good at maintaining regular exercise, healthy eating and sleeping habits. On the horizontal axis, self-validation refers to how and where a person receives information about his or her identity or who he or she is as a person. The right side represents "Internal Validation," referring to a person who is confident in their internal belief system and relies on their own self-awareness to make decisions.

Developing "Internal Validation" requires the definition of values and goals for oneself and then following through on them. For example, a person who doesn't care about how he appears to others on Facebook, states what he believes regardless of the number of likes. The left side represents "External Validation"; that is, a person prone to seek the approval and admiration of others to feel a sense of value. In the Facebook example, this is a person who looks to others and changes his behavior based on how his status will increase. External validation can be unpredictable and temporary as the person in that category is, in most cases, unable to control the validation. So behavior induced by external validation is likely to be ad hoc and not sustainable in the long run.

In this 2 x 2 matrix [Figure 1], the upper right quadrant is the "Independent" profile, which is the final destination recommended in the Model. The lower left quadrant is the "Submissive" profile, from which departure is encouraged. Thus, either via lower right quadrant, which represents the "Tension" profile or upper left quadrant, which represents the "Limit" profile, the person will arrive at the "Independent" profile.

The "Tension" profile, lower right quadrant, refers to someone who has Internal Validation, but has low capability of Self-Regulation. People who fall in this profile are earnest enough to set up their high-level principles, values and beliefs, but they often fail to follow them. This Model attributes this failure to vague standards of effective monitoring to ob-

Figure 1. Independency Model

jectively know how they are doing. This provides insufficient energy to sustain their willpower and fails to motivate them to meet a high standard. While this type of persona has internal approval, they have high expectations of themselves and they constantly have to deal with a certain degree of guilt and shame. They frequently struggle internally, and go back and forth between working hard and feeling a sense of failure.

The "Limit" profile, upper left quadrant, refers to someone who seeks External Validation, and has a high capability of Self-Regulation. People who are categorized in this profile have resources to control themselves and are good at adhering to a desired habit once the goal is clearly articulated. They can autonomously create plans and milestones to achieve their goal and follow the path they establish. "Limit" profiles have an effective way to monitor their progress and know how to maintain their energy level to keep going. However, since they are highly dependent on obtaining approval and endorsement from others, they are susceptible to authority or trends. In this regards, they can be dependent on wearable devices, which act as external validation. If not device specific, then social media re-affirmation plays an important role. Because of accessibility, broad usage and immediacy, it has become increasingly easier to obtain external validation through social media. Research suggests that this dependency pushes people towards addictive online usage and external validation is one important factor relating to this (Young 1998, Griffiths 2000, Song et. al. 2004). [5][6][7] In the context of health and wellbeing, achieving temporary goals is part of a positive strategy for some, but the key is continuous re-evaluation working toward longer-term sustainable goals.

The "Independent" profile, upper right quadrant, refers to people who are independent and in control of constant physical activities, healthy sleep and food intake habits. They care about totally balanced mind and body health. They have their own lasting principles about quality of life that is based on human interaction, thus are not influenced by short-term

trends and fashion. They know all about the latest technologies and open to try them, but won't succumb to the lure of tech dominance over human or physical interaction. They are also socially and intellectually active and emotionally mature so that their healthy habits rarely run into conflict with occupational, social, family or community obligations.

The "Submissive" profile, lower left quadrant, refers to people who are dependent on external validation and have a low capability of self-regulation. This is the most challenging group to motivate as it requires an "entrance" strategy. Post "entrance," these consumers must choose a path either through "Tension" or "Limit" to get to "Independence."

Design principles for each profile to help move toward Independence

Among these four different profiles, "Tension" and "Limit" are typically current users of wearable activity tracking devices [Figure 2]. "Submissive" is the least preferable profile and a path of departure from this profile is strongly encouraged, "Independent," "Tension" and "Limit" are the groups for which wearable activity tracking devices certainly assist to great advantages. However, long-term goals of stable change and internalization of healthy habits, require a built-in approach toward Independence.

For "Submissive" types: an entrance strategy is needed as they are not willing to try to make changes in their lives. This modification of behavior may require a single shocking trigger. However, a trigger may create an unnecessary distraction. - (Fogg, 2009). Since this profile shows no movement by simply being presented their current habits and goal settings, there are two ways to measure the change in their behavior. One is to entice them by visualizing a positive future so that they can see themselves post-effects as being more admired and respected. This increases the likelihood to evolve to the "Limit" profile, whereby people also value external vali-

dations. Another path is to show a negative consequence, which is the brutal result of long-term unhealthy behavior. This will likely drive them to adopt the "Limit" or "Tension" behavior.

For "Tension" types: while struggling and bouncing around, this profile seeks a balanced approach to life. Wearable activity tracking devices push the user to set achievable goals while heavily emphasizing support through quick positive motivational encouragement. This reminder model works to motivate people into a more active encounter. The key is that the reminder has to be contextualized and appear at the perfect time. Therefore, these cues require intelligence and behavior monitoring, which is highly context sensitive based on schedule, work status and psychological state of the users.

For "Limit" types: those in the "Limit" profile have always had an easy time setting their own boundaries. They are often the ones setting controls. Given their reliance on external standards for appropriate behavior, they respond well to coaching input. A coach offers personal motivation to help him/her to accomplish a specific target. This method assumes the person will continue with the practice he/she learned (which is most often the case with these pleaser personalities). Short-term goals, however, have to be quickly translated to long-term goals. By showing long-term effects of negative behavior, the "Limit" profile can be encouraged to take a longer view toward a healthy lifestyle. The goal has to be a higher level and superordinate. Superordinate level goals are thought to contribute to a more profound and lasting motivational experience than focal-level goals [8]. Because superordinate goals reflect the principles that individuals value [8], researching these higher-level goals may show how exercise fits into an individual's greater life objectives and their personal goal structures [9].

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE STUDY

Although still in its early and conceptual phase, the Independence Model (IM) provides a comprehensive view of people's health related behavior primarily in the context of wearable tracking device usage. It suggests a path to liberate people from their dependency of these devices. [Figure 3.] This is what we encourage those designing these products and services do in order to secure the long-term health of their users. True independence or a holistic healthy life state requires that technology invite people to recognize current behavior and internalize healthier habits rather than relying on permanent usage of such technological devices. This is an initial proposal for further study. The effectiveness of each design criteria and detailed mechanism and path for people to eventually graduate to Independence is yet to be fully researched both qualitatively and quantitatively.

Figure 2. Wearable activity tracking devices can be helpful "Tension" and "Limit" profiles

Figure 3. Two alternate paths to "Independent". A wearable device should employ both "Entrance" and "Exit" strategies

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RESEARCH METHODOLOGY FOR DESIGN OF HIGH FUNCTIONAL COMPLEXITY CLOTHING

Fausto Alonso Zuleta Montoya*, Ángela María Echeverri Jaramillo, Blanca Lucia Echavarría Bustamante
 Facultad de Diseño de Vestuario
 Escuela de Arquitectura y Diseño
 Universidad Pontificia Bolivariana
 ✉ fausto.zuleta@upb.edu.co*

ABSTRACT

Following the purposes of the Clothing Design program, which emphasize research processes that explore clothing from different areas, from the materials to production, the project is presented within the field of the exploration of clothing as mediator between the body (acknowledging it as an internal system) and its special context (as an external system). Both systems demand specific and ascertainable requirements that have been determined through research and that will answer through high complexity clothing developed for a specific sport, in this particular case artistic and rhythmic gymnastics.

KEYWORDS: *Clothing design, movement analysis, gymnastics clothing.*

INTRODUCTION

The Universidad Pontificia Bolivariana's Clothing Design Faculty and the Fundación Universitaria María Cano Movement Analysis Laboratory (both located in Medellín) combined academic resources that would allow the development of research projects within social and business sectors. The project "Design and Construction of High Functional Complexity Clothing (technical proposal and construction of new clothes for high performance in sports)" was executed in 2013, with the purpose of making clothes that meet specific sports requirements, in this case rhythmic and artistic gymnastics. This project has been developed in two phases involving technical progress in sports and social areas that become smart solutions for developing high functional clothing. The first phase involved the research method that resulted in the design of sports clothes. The second phase, aimed to develop an analysis of the clothes and the athlete. This article presents the results of the research that are relevant to the Clothing Design and Textiles Research Group (GIDVT) of the Universidad Pontificia Bolivariana.

CONCEPTS

In order to understand the intention of a research project that combines the development of the so-called "high complexity" clothes and the analysis of clothes within the field

of ergonomics science, it is enough to observe the requirements of the case study. These requirements involve the user, the context in which he operates and the clothing product transversally. The difference with other fashion or clothing research projects is that the result is not an adaptive and commercially productive creation but instead it seeks to harbor the most determining solution for a specific need of the case study. This is called high complexity clothing because it interacts with the user's needs within an activity in a demanding context and is not seeking to be commercially viable, since the solution, the activity and the context are what determine the productive aspects of the aforementioned clothing.

High complexity clothing:

"High complexity clothing" refers to clothing development that seeks functional and technical solutions and that within its pattern design does not obey any commercial productive system (Zapata, 2013). Within this concept, the term "technical" fabric for sportswear appears but it can be combined with different functional variables. In order to better understand the term high complexity clothing, we need to relate the products of various brands in the sports industry and the laboratories used in the study and testing of the best possible clothing. These brands undertake much research and development for sports shoes, jerseys, sweatshirts, jackets and accessories for different sports. Brands like Nike, Adidas, Speedo and Columbia Sportswear have their research laboratories, in partnership with universities, technology

centers or industries, to develop highly complex clothing for universal sports such as football, basketball, tennis, golf and swimming among others (Sherman, 2011). High performance military uniforms are another example of this. The purpose of these technical fabrics is to produce high complexity clothing to stimulate the evaporation of perspiration during or after sports in a moderately hot environment. In many cases, these clothes do not provide any thermo regulating, physiological or comfort advantage when compared to traditional cotton clothes, as they have not been made using new technological materials (with memory of form, antibacterial, thermoregulation, etc.) However, a good proposal for anatomic, anthropometric, composition and function response for using clothing made with so-called technological fabrics may benefit and control the physical conditions of the user. This is why techniques for pattern design and the laboratories set up to determine multiple variables are vital in the development and fabrication of clothes intended to help the final performance of the clothing (Fernández, 2013). A research study undertaken at the University of Indiana demonstrated the different implications for high complexity clothing (Med Sci Sports Exerc 2001 Dec 33(12), pp2124-2130). High complexity clothing is not only specified in technological fabrics but also in the important physiological variables and its anthropometrical constructive connotations. Practicing their sport, raises athletes' body temperature (e.g. Skin temperature, central temperature, and heart rate and sweat loss). These variables, together with biochemical analyses and laboratories are used for the design and construction of the clothing. Thus, it is called "high complexity clothing" as it includes all the factors for optimum and comfortable design (Bartels, 2005).

Thermoregulatory Clothing:

One of the best characteristics of high complexity clothing is thermoregulation as this is a determining factor for the good or bad condition of the user in the context in which he is performing. Using sportswear for high competition as a reference point, a correlation between the confection cluster, design and textile industry can be established. The latter, the textile industry, has slowly reacted to the big opportunities that micro-encapsulation has to offer, defining it as the inclusion of materials using very small matrices to be liberated later and gradually (Villena, 2009). Currently, the number of phase change material (PCM) commercial applications in the textile industry continues to grow to give new properties and added value to the final products, such as: medical fabrics or technical fabrics for sports.

Clothes with micro-encapsulation can improve a person's level of thermic comfort because they can solve the heat exchange between the human body and its surroundings (Shelton, 2009). Unexpected temperature surges in the environment or human body as happens with athletes (because of muscular cooling, fever, hormonal changes or organ heating), lead to a thermal imbalance between the body and its surroundings, generating a feeling of discomfort.

Clothes capable of absorbing or emitting heat to the body according to external stimuli may help rapid thermoregulation and a sense of wellbeing, they may also help with energy recovery or controlled energy release, which is known as thermoregulatory clothing.

METHODOLOGY

The project's first phase involved a systematic search by teachers and students approaching an exploration for a monograph. The search explored sport norms, regulations, state of art and timelines, as a research approach indicated by Dorst (2001, 2008) and Jones (1970). In these methods, the approach is based on the collection of theoretical information, which can put together solid project requirements (route 1). A parallel fieldwork project was organized in order to gain knowledge about the sport and the athlete. This research project was ethnographic and brought to the research process closer to the user-context reality (route 2). The case study was divided taking into account the user categories that were established by the context: rhythmic and artistic category, open and women categories and infant, junior and masters categories. In this fieldwork, determining the application approach to the environment to be treated, the biomechanics fundamentals and the clothes that work as prosthesis for the improvement of the activity. These studies merge with the response of textile bases that make up the suit to develop and offer several aids to improve development (Adequacy Filters for route 1 & 2). In the case of suits as prosthesis, this union compliments the development of a simple activity (lift up, walk, grab, and support, among others); however, there is too much to be developed in this field and the research analysis and results can be taken to a more efficient level, when talking about clothing (Shishoo, 2005). This entire methodological framework can be seen in Figure 1.

With this process, we can see that the methodology has a theoretical and explorative approach, according to the scope that is used today in research. These investigative approaches of the project are based on high complexity costume design and provide the basis for the early stages of product development. It is noteworthy that the methodology has come to be completed in stage I, which is determined using research tools for the project, but has not been validated. We are now in Phase II, where the validation and review of laboratory project (FUMC) is undertaken for performance.

The first part allows us to find that the technical basis and the high complexity related to the type of stroke and cuts that have been taken into account to build these types of suits, such as the confection techniques, are far from being the best possible solution for functional high complexity clothing, that's why we built different prototypes and tests in the first phase of the research process. Researchers determined the strains of functional sportswear (Hamill, 2003) (Scott, 2005) (Shishoo, 2005) with which they proved their point that designing the functional high complex suit as a simple creative

Fig. 1. Research process methodology applied to product development

and aesthetic exercise is not enough, it also has to involve responding to a profound knowledge of anatomy, anthropometry, composition and functional response of the technological fabrics, sports physics, and in some special cases design pattern techniques and the use of the laboratory to detect multiple variables. All of this showed the relevance and reach of this research project, and helped in the process and physical activity research phase, which provided the scope for the clothing project. The needs for the development of the clothing were investigated with a theory of applied research, a conceptualization theory, a production theory and a development workshop (Lipovetsky, 1990) (Lurie, 1994) (Vilsser, 2009). It is important to establish that in the research process, we took into account the stress points of the materials, the internal and external forces in the human body and other requirements driven from the impact of the person in action this is being validated with the FUMC (which is in process, as phase II).

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

For the development of a high complexity clothing project, any analysis between the user-context-product must be a matter for investigation, as must the particularity of each aspect, individually and as a set. The final objectives of the suit are determined by this analysis and are materialized when they are transferred to the business and social environment. All of this resulted in the creation of various designs that focused on the user and analysis category detailed in the case study (See example in figure 2).

The search for the maximum comfort for those users in their contexts arises as the physical and technological challenge

Figure 2. Clothing artistic gymnasts category, male-older. Paths of muscular work: Ricardo Zapata. Photo: Esteban Gutierrez. Gymnast: William Calle (UPB copyright).

for specific high performance activities. This has led to these types of suits becoming more efficient and allowing athletes a better performance, which, in turn, is becoming an important focal point for further research.

In the first phase of the project, the intentions were directed towards the gymnastics field and to competitive purposes. A research process has been developed that involves different actors in highly competitive gymnastics (athletes, national leagues, physiotherapist, sports physiologists and biomedical engineers) in accordance to the possibilities or advice necessary for the development of high performance clothing. In this activity, we proposed the biomechanical analysis to help the material formalization of new suits that grant bigger benefits in their use. The investigation perspective involves social and technological aspects, understanding these fields within movement analysis and the development of new functional high complexity clothing that may aid the improvement of specific activities in different sports.

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PICK A PERSON USER INSIGHT AND DESIGN FOR WELLBEING THROUGH PERSONALITY PSYCHOLOGY

John Magnus Roos
Veryday
Centre for Consumer Science, University of Gothenburg
✉ Magnus.Roos@Veryday.com

Diana Africano Clark
Veryday
✉ Diana.Africano.Clark@Veryday.com

ABSTRACT

In this paper we describe a non-verbal personality instrument for user-centred design that consists of 10 extreme cartoon-like characters. The theoretical framework for the characters is The Big Five personality model: openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism. Each of the five dimensions has two extremities; open-minded versus closed-minded; conscientious versus impulsive; extrovert versus introvert; agreeable versus antagonistic; neurotic versus emotionally stable. During explorative interviews the user is free to pick the personality character(s) that correspond to who he or she is at present when interacting with a certain product, service, system or environment. Additionally the user picks the characters that correspond to who he/she would ideally like to be when interacting with the same research object. The aim of the method is to provide insight into what design aspects may bridge the gap that resides in the mismatch between the individual's real and ideal self, thereby facilitating wellbeing-driven design.

KEYWORDS: *pictorial, non-verbal, personality, self, user-centered design*

INTRODUCTION

Psychologists have a long tradition of developing personality tests that measure who people are. These tests have mostly been used by recruiting agencies and Public Health Institutions in order to predict health problems and addictive behaviour. Nowadays, verbal personality tests are increasingly used in quantitative business and design studies in order to receive insights about user behaviour (i.e. Sing & Das, 2009; Xu & Montague, 2012; Roos, 2013). Verbal personality tests usually consist of a large number of statements, sometimes several pages, in which the user responds to what level he or she agrees or disagrees. So far, personality tests have not been associated with qualitative user-studies, simply because they have not been designed for such purposes. The present study argues that reshaping and adjusting these personality tests to be more user-study might create new opportunities for user input in people-driven design, especially when the focus is on subjective wellbeing and personal growth.

PERSONALITY THEORIES

The real self and the ideal self

The central concepts in Carl Roger's theory of personality are the real self and the ideal self. The real self consists of all the ideas, perceptions and values that characterize "I" or "me"; it includes the awareness of "what I am". The ideal self is our conception of the kind of person we would like to be. Our perceived real and ideal selves very seldom match. The inevitable gap that this mismatch generates causes various degrees of unpleasant affect and health problems. A greater understanding of what is at each end of this personal polarity, and extensively what bridges it, gives us new tools to design for subjective wellbeing. According to Roger (1951), the closer the real self is to the ideal self, the more fulfilled and happy the individual becomes. A large discrepancy between the real self and the ideal self results in an unhappy and dissatisfied person (Atkinson et al, 2000).

The Big Five

The Big Five is the taxonomy of personality traits that has received the most attention and support from personality researchers and personality theorists. According to the Big Five model, all human characters can be categorized into five broad personality dimensions; Openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness and neuroticism (Larsen and Buss, 2005). According to Larsen and Buss (2005), key markers of the Big Five are as follows:

1. **Openness (versus reticence).** Open individuals are open for innovations, different cultures and the emotions of other people, while closed individuals are more conservative and closed in terms of the emotions of other people.
2. **Conscientiousness (versus impulsivity).** Conscientious individuals are industrious and think ahead. They are organized, neat and prompt, while spontaneous people are more careless and disorderly.
3. **Extraversion (versus introversion).** Extroverts love to party, they engage in frequent social interaction, take the lead in livening up dull gatherings, and enjoy talking a lot. Introverts are more shy and quiet, and tend to be more like wallflowers.
4. **Agreeableness (versus disagreeableness).** Agreeable individuals get along well with others, are well liked, avoid conflicts, strive for harmony, while disagreeable people are aggressive, unsympathetic and seem to get themselves into a lot of social conflicts.
5. **Neuroticism (versus emotional stability).** Emotionally stable individuals are calm, relaxed and stable, while emotionally unstable individuals are moody, anxious and insecure.

A NON-VERBAL PERSONALITY TOOL

Development of the tool

Our ambition has been to create unisexual and multicultural characters, free from physical objects and symbols (e.g. clothes and hairstyles). We have combined personality theories with knowledge regarding body language and facial expressions (i.e. Axtell, 1998; Ekman and Friesen, 2003; Navarro and Karllins, 2008; Pease and Pease, 2004), and used Internet and comic magazines as inspiration.

Different versions of the characters have been tested in six different pilot studies ($n \approx 20$ student per study) at the University of Gothenburg and Stockholm University, and continuously improved by graphic designers at Veryday, a design agency in Sweden. Altogether we have developed ten personality characters and one neutral (Figure 1). The first five characters (e.g. closed-minded, impulsive, extrovert, antagonistic and neurotic) have been validated against 143 undergraduate Swedish students at the University of Gothenburg. Their counterparts (e.g. open-minded, conscientious, introvert, agreeable, emotionally stable) have only been validated against 32 under-

Figure 1. Ten non-verbal personality characters and neutral.

graduate Swedish students at the University of Gothenburg. We view the validation of the counterparts as a pilot study.

Validation of the tool

The validation process included content validity, criterion validity and construct validity (Laurans, 2011). The content validation of the non-verbal scale is based on tag clouds of adjectives from top-of-mind responses (i.e. responses to the question “*which three adjectives do you best think describe this person?*”). The tag clouds have been compared to the general framework of the Big Five model of personalities. The criterion validation of the non-verbal scale is based on the equivalence between this scale and an established verbal scale of the Big Five model of personalities, the HP5i (Gustavsson, Jönsson, Linder and Weinryb, 2008; Holmberg and Weibull, 2010). In the validation process, the perceived personality of each character was measured by all HP5-15 items (Table 1). The scale used for each item was a four-level scale; completely agree (coded as 1), partly agree (coded as 2), partly disagree (coded as 3), completely disagree (coded as 4). For the criterion validity to be satisfactory, the three items measuring the particular factor must have an average of 1,5 (i.e. between completely agree and partly agree). Construct validity refers to how the extremities are constructed and how they differ from each other. Ideally, the items used to measure one extremity should be as different as possible but have high correlation among themselves (convergent validity) while the correlations between different extremities (and items) should be as low as possible (divergent validity). Also the construct validation of the non-verbal scale is based on convergent validity and divergent validity in relation to HP5i. For the convergent validity to be satisfactory, the correlation

PERSONALITY TRAIT	ITEMS IN HP5
Openness (reverse scale)	I think emotions are often exaggerated
	I often have difficulties in understanding other's feelings
	Normally, I avoid getting involved in others' problems
Conscientiousness (reverse scale)	I usually act on the spur of the moment
	I often throw myself too hastily into things
	I usually talk before I think
Extraversion	I often feel exhilarated
	I usually enjoy life
	I am usually in a good mood when I socialize
Agreeableness (reverse scale)	I often make sarcastic remarks
	I usually behave vengefully if I am treated badly
	I usually come up with piercing and malicious answers
Neuroticism	I often feel uncomfortable and ill at ease
	I often feel pressure when I have to speed up
	My muscles are often so tense that I get tired

Table 1. Link between personality dimensions and items
Source: Gustavsson, Jönsson, Linder and Weinryb, 2008; Holmberg and Weibull, 2010

of the three items measuring a particular dimension (Table 1) should be as high as possible. But they also have to capture the broadness of that specific dimension (for instance openness), rather than measuring the same thing. For the divergent validity to be satisfactory, the mean of the three items (Table 1) should correspond more to the dimension it is supposed to measure than to other dimensions. In other words, the dimensions should be mutually exclusive.

The validation process of the first five characters has been presented at five international conferences (Roos, 2012a; 2012b; 2013; 2014; Roos, Nilsson & Whetley, 2013). To summarize our findings, the neurotic character scores high on all three validity measures. The extrovert character and the antagonistic character scored low on content validity. The impulsive character scored low on construct validity. The most problematic character was the closed-minded, which scored low on both validity and construct validity.

GENERAL DISCUSSION

Currently we validate all 10 characters (Figure 1). We have made some modifications of the first five since the last validation (Roos, 2013), in order to receive higher criterion validity. We have also added a neutral character, to be used in the introduction of the test in order to avoid the perception of the first character to be influenced by general characteristics, such as hairless and undressed. We also worked with the graphic design aesthetics in order to synchronize the eleven characters. The shape of faces and hands differ somewhat (Figure 1), which might have threatened our effort to develop unisexual and multicultural characters.

The reason for our ambitious validation effort was, and is, that we would like to cover the variety in human beings. The Big Five model has successfully been able to capture the variety in humanity, across time and cultures (Larsen & Buss, 2005). If we are able to develop a non-verbal personality tool that corresponds to the Big Five personality model, we are able to give the respondents a simple, but still comprehensive, tool to express themselves.

Despite an ambitious validation effort, we are not searching for an ultimate truth shared by all individuals. When using the instrument, the primary focus is not to find out whom a person is through his or her life, based on some kind of scientific objectivity. We do not think that such truths exist in either verbal or non-verbal languages (e.g. facial expressions and body language). The advantages of using the characters are that they open up discussions in an interview context and help researchers interact and uncover aspects of use, tacit knowledge, and latent needs that users are otherwise unwilling and/or unable to verbally express. This is especially true when it comes to associations, personal desires, needs and feelings, and when it comes to anticipations of the future as opposed to reflections of the past. So far, the characters have been used as “personality cards”, especially in explorative research settings (Roos, Nilsson & Whetley, 2013). The users are free to interpret the characters, and we primarily focus on why the users pick and combine specific cards,

We believe that designers, as well as psychologists, can contribute to subjective wellbeing, but first they have to know what makes people happy. We use the personality cards to explore potential discrepancies between the user's real self and ideal self (Roos, Nilsson & Whetley, 2013). Such input

helps us design for the user's wellbeing in accordance with Carl Roger's self-theory (1951). Our experience is that the personality cards make it easier for users to express who they are, both in general and in relation to the study object. Our experience is that the cards also make it easier for users to talk about their ideal self, or who they want to be, both in the world they perceive and in the world they dream about. The users' dreams and aspirations open up for business opportunities, both related to individual- and environmental change. Therefore, the input can stimulate all kind of design solutions (i.e. product-, service-, interactive-, digital solutions).

Unlike existing personality tests, this test is adjusted for interviews and co-creation sessions, and combines the real and ideal selves, rather than only focusing on the real self. Unlike current non-verbal tools used in the design field (e.g. SAM emotional response measurement manikin, PrEmo measure product emotions), this tool focuses more on aspirations within individuals rather than appraisals of stimuli.

CONCLUSION

Our conclusion is that the pictorial characters help users to express their personality, which might not always be easy to do with the use of words alone. However, the validation process of the ten characters is not yet completed and more effort is needed in order to investigate to what degree the presented pictorial assessment actually corresponds to the theoretical framework of the Big Five.

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RESEARCH MINI-MUSEUM

Shivani Mohan
Facebook, Inc.
✉ mohanshivani@fb.com

ABSTRACT

This use-case describes the construction of a temporary small-scale museum-like space to display visual research artifacts such as annotated paper prototypes, card sorting, word exercises and interview footage to create new forms of interaction with qualitative research within an organization.

KEYWORDS: *Qualitative research, Research artifacts, Display, Museum, Presentation, Data Dissemination*

INTRODUCTION

As researchers, we have an ever-expanding arsenal of ways to understand people's behavior and attitudes towards Internet services. We can perform usability studies, have participants mark-up paper prototypes, and gather screen shots of the product experience from small "dogfooding" groups, to name just a few methods.

Internet services also need fast research and analysis cycles to allow for rapid product development. As researchers, we are in charge of analyzing more and more qualitative and quantitative data and quickly turning it into actionable insights so that product teams can make informed decisions.

CHALLENGES IN DISSEMINATING RESEARCH

While it's possible to cull many data points into a concise presentation, a lot of valuable detail is banished into the archive section. In addition, the insights are usually only presented to a small group – usually the specific group deciding on product direction.

This is not a new problem: researchers in many different areas of specialization have explored novel ways to disseminate research in a way that preserves detail and encourages access. Some of the successful experiments in qualitative data dissemination incorporate 'the arts' as a method of data shar-

ing. *The 7,024th Patient* [1] used an exhibition of poetry and artistic visuals to immerse audiences in patient experiences. Similarly, *Handle with Care? Women living with Metastatic Breast Cancer* [2] was a research based theatre production aiming to share the lives and concerns of women living with breast cancer.

The above methods though evocative and impactful, are time consuming and thus difficult to implement in a culture that relies on speed and agility: namely Internet services.

This use case explores a way to:

1. *Broaden the reach of UEX research:* Distribute research insights to more people within an organization, not just the specific group deciding product direction.
2. *Preserve detail:* Create a way for research artifacts to be viewed in their raw form.
3. *Craft novel experiences:* Create new interactions with qualitative research within an organization.

OUR PROJECT

The Facebook research team conducted a ten-day study with twelve participants to get foundational insights for a new product we are building. This research included: a set of twelve preliminary interviews to set up the study, asynchronous dscout feedback during the week (dScout is a mobile application that allows research participants to share im-

ages and screenshots on their smartphones directly with a researcher), and follow up interviews where participants responded to design stimuli.

After conducting all of the research sessions, we had a large number of data rich research artifacts:

- 153 snippets of user screenshots and their comments from dscout
- 24 card sorts
- 30 participant annotated paper prototypes
- 12 word exercise sheets
- 12 Likert scales with participant notes and reasons

While analyzing the insights that emerged from all these data points, we wondered whether there was any way that the whole product team, and perhaps even other product teams could look at all these research artifacts in their raw form. We felt that the users' own handwritten comments and feedback, as well as screenshots of the product being used in their day to day lives could be far more impactful than a succinct PowerPoint deck. We wanted to create a format of dissemination that allowed for interaction, slow musing and time for discussion and interpretation.

THE MINI-MUSEUM

Our solution was to construct a small-scale temporary museum, which was focused entirely on our research. Also, since research and development cycles are short, we had to devise a way to put up this exhibition in half a business day. This is how we constructed the space:

- We used an empty workspace with pods of desks to create this museum space.
- *Horizontal display spaces:* Tables served as horizontal display spaces to place the research artifacts. We used these surfaces to display participant card sorting images; paper prototypes with handwritten user annotations, 153 dscout snippet printouts, word exercises and annotated likert scales. We placed large numbers on each desk so that people could navigate the space and follow our narrative (See figure 1.).
- *Vertical display spaces.* We decided to put the high level insights and section titles on vertical displays so that people could see what insights we drew from the raw data in front of them. Since this was a low fidelity set up, we got creative and decided to re-use 'caution wet floor' signs as the vertical display system (See figure 2.).
- *Streaming video:* We used monitors on some of the tables to stream video footage of the research sessions pertinent to the artifact displayed so that the context in which the research artifact was made was clear (See figure 3.).
- Lastly, an event invitation was sent out to the entire product vertical.

Figure 1. The image above illustrates the use of workstations as makeshift display spaces. Here we have displayed annotated paper prototypes.

Figure 2. The image above provides an example of a quick hack for putting together a vertical display for the Research Mini-Museum. This is a 'caution wet floor' sign mounted with paper.

Figure 3. The image above displays our set up with the tables containing images of participant card sorts, and a monitor streaming video of participants sharing their rationale for why they grouped certain cards together.

RESPONSE TO THE MINI-MUSEUM:

- In less than 48 hours, there were 83 RSVPs to the invitations sent out for the Mini-Museum opening. Over the course of the week that the Mini-Museum was up and running, over a 100 people visited the space and interacted with the research artifacts. This was our biggest research turn out yet, and had less notice than any other event. This was also the first time some of the engineers who had been working on this product heard and read feedback from end users. (See figure 4.)
- This format allowed for cross-pollination of research and ideas: we had people from different product groups visit the Mini-Museum and discover ideas that could impact the products they were building. This is often a pain point in large organizations: it is challenging to share research across different product verticals.
- This display format spawned multiple requests to display other research projects in a similar way. In response, our research team plans to socialize this format so that more teams are aware of this option.

Figure 4. The image above displays the Mini-Museum in use.

LEARNINGS FOR FUTURE ITERATIONS:

This new data dissemination system opened up the world of qualitative research to new audiences and some of the research methods we used (such as card sorting and dScout snippets) were not as self-explanatory as we imagined. We noticed that the value of the Mini-Museum was greater when there was a researcher present to answer some of the research methodology related questions.

The artifacts within the Mini-Museum often spawned many ideas and solutions to user stated problems, as well as follow up research questions. In the future, we will work on creating an idea-bank to capture solutions and serve as repositories of ideas for further research.

Lastly, for the long term, we are evaluating whether it would be valuable to turn the Mini-Museum into a permanent space within our organization. This space would be dedicated to sharing different research findings on a regular basis with anyone who is interested in the voice of the end user.

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»TAP ANYTHING« A DESIGN (CLASS) CASE: TEACHING PARTICIPATORY DESIGN METHODS AS DESIGN BASICS

Monika Hoinkis
University of Applied Sciences Potsdam
✉ hoinkis@fh-potsdam.de

ABSTRACT

This report looks at a higher education design class as a design case for teaching participatory design methods to beginning design students from different design disciplines (communication, product, and interface design). The class was an experiment in so far as basic design education usually focuses on other elementary aspects first, such as form, color, representation, etc. The experiment's purpose was to confront design students very early on in the program with a participatory design approach and find out how well they can handle and apply it and how valuable it is for their basic design education. The report describes the overall aim, structure, process, and outcomes of the design class at University of Applied Sciences Potsdam and takes a peek into the near future.

KEYWORDS: *design methods, co-design, teaching design, education, prototyping*

INTRODUCTION

During the winter semester of 2013/14, from October to February, a design class at University of Applied Sciences Potsdam (FHP) took place that explored teaching participatory design methods and approaches to first and second year design students. The aim of the class was twofold: firstly, it was all about learning and applying design methods, mainly the participatory design method but also related methods from user-centered design such as ethnography, probes, usability testing, etc. We pretty much undertook a 'journey' through Liz Sander's 'Topography of Design Research' (2006, fig. 1). Whereas later on in design education it is important to choose the design method well and wisely, and the student should be able to explain why he or she used this particular method, in the design basics approach described in this report the aim was to get in touch with different methods in a light and playful way, to get to know them and have them on ones skill-palette for future design projects.

The class was project-oriented, so along with the participatory design approach there was also a specific subject matter: the class was named 'Alles mal antatschen', German for 'tap anything', after a rather cynical article about interactive

children's books (Wellershoff 2013). We explored the use of the Smartboard, or Digital Whiteboard (e.g. Mimio 2014), and its possibilities in the classroom from a design perspective, as classrooms are massively upgraded with this technology today. Teachers though often lack time, ideas and knowledge to deploy it fruitfully and creatively in class. For example, in an interview we learned that one math teacher spent a whole summer designing an interactive application for the Smartboard. Surely designers can help here!

DESIGN BRIEF

The task for the design students was to design an interactive learning or reading application for the Smartboard to be used in a primary school class. Target group: primary school kids, 1–4 years old. Implementation: prototype with interactive features to run on the actual Smartboard in the primary school classroom. Method: deploying a participatory design process (Sanders 2004, 2013), getting in touch and in conversation with future users and target groups (pupils and teachers), doing 'fieldwork', doing user-centered design.

DESIGN PROCESS

Thus, the students design process was structured in nine main consecutive and interacting steps:

1. Expert input
2. Preliminary interviews
3. Observation
4. Ideas and prototypes
5. Testing
6. Participatory workshop
7. Iteration
8. Presentation
9. Feedback

Below the process from step 1 to 7 is visualized as a flow chart (fig. 1) and mapped onto Sander's 'Topology of Design Research' (fig.2).

From design question through several steps in the design process to the design answer/outcome

Expert Input

To start off we got an introduction to teaching with Smartboards and to the technology in general from our partner school (Grundschule im Bornstedter Feld 2013) and a company who releases digital animated primers for a mutual reading experience in the classroom (Onilo, 2013).

Figure 1. Structure and Process of the Design Class.

Preliminary Interviews

Students conducted interviews with teachers and/or pupils among their acquaintances with a participatory/ideation element in the form of a design probe (Gaver et al 1999, see fig. 4).

Observation

To learn through the method of observing, students sat in classes and watched the application of Smartboards carefully. We undertook the observation in a different school in Berlin (Rixdorfer Schule 2013) to experience a different demographic (more pupils with migration backgrounds, less financially strong families compared to the school in Potsdam).

Figure 2. Topography of Design Research after Sanders (2006), numbers show the according step in our design process.

Figure 4. Design Probes Used in the Interviews: 'draw what you would like to see on a magic board in the classroom'.

Figure 5. Observing the Use of the Smartboard and Other Details in the Classroom.

Figure 6. Lo-fi Testing of the Prototypes with Paper Prototyping and Click-through on Laptops and TVs.

Ideas and Prototypes

Based on expert input, interviews and observation in the field, first ideas, concepts, and designs for interactive Smartboard learning applications emerged. To be able to go into further discussions with the target group prototypes were necessary. Since there were several first-year students in the group, the method to implement the prototypes had to be simple and quick to learn. We chose to use Apple's Keynote application for quick building of interactive prototypes (e.g. Keynotopia 2013) as it requires very little previous knowledge and students today are already familiar with presentation software like Keynote or PowerPoint from presentations they are making in high school classes. The results were highly useful 'clickable' prototypes we could use for the next phase.

Testing

Over the Christmas holidays, about halfway through the semester, students had to conduct a private usability test with

their prototypes with friends and family at home. Like in a classic usability test they tested design, understanding, interaction and interface design and also retrieved open comments and ideas for their concepts and prototypes. The test settings varied: as we could not test on the actual classroom, Smartboard students used their laptops, TVs, occasionally projections, as well as paper prototypes to walk children through their ideas. The outcome was analyzed and put into writing for further utilization.

Participatory Workshop

Preparation: Parallel to the testing a big workshop on site in the school was organized and prepared. Preparing the workshop was an essential part of the class. The aim was to convey that the preparation was as much an act of designing as designing the prototypes, the actual design product. Students developed themselves a concept for the workshop and produced very creative tools and guidelines to run the workshop (see fig. 7).

Figure 7. Tools, Questionnaires and Guidelines for the Workshop.

Figure 8. 'Testing-Groups: Kids Trying Out the Prototypes, Effective and Funny Rating System Using Cardboard Plates with Smiley Faces.

Figure 9. 'Ideation-Groups: Augmenting Paper Prototypes with Features, Drawing Fantasy Smartboards and Game Playing.

Workshop: The workshop took place one afternoon in early January 2014, from 2:00 to 4:00 p.m. The participants were 40 school-kids (ages 1–4 and 6–11), 3 teachers, 21 workshop organizers (19 university students, 2 university teachers). The kids were divided into four groups and there was one additional teacher group. Each group was accompanied by 3–4 design students.

Group 1 and 2: Testing

Groups showed prototypes on the Smartboard in the classroom and talked about them with the kids. The kids were the 'jury' and were asked to rate certain aspects (legibility, color, fun, etc.) with a special rating system. Kids could also come to the boards, interact with the prototypes, and make comments (see fig. 8).

Group 3 and 4: Ideation

Groups played games to learn about the children's interests and let them draw on 'magic Smartboards' or add fantasy features to their existing prototypes (see fig. 9). The groups were very colorful, noisy, creatively messy, and merry.

Group 5: Teacher focus group

There was a round-table discussion and brainstorming with teachers about several topics that came up in the design process, such as: what were the obstacles while using the Smartboards, what worked, what did not, was the technical and infrastructure supportive so that they could build applications themselves, what could be improved, etc.

Each group had a session of 20 minutes and then alternated rooms, so every group was in every room once (except the teacher group).

Iteration

Findings, inspirations, and new ideas from the workshop were again analyzed, put into writing and then together with the private testing results used for an iteration of the existing prototypes. The changes that were made to the prototypes varied. Some only changed details, colors, illustration styles, etc.; others changed their concept much more profoundly, and some even completely discarded their concept and developed a new one.

PRESENTATION AND FEEDBACK

Three weeks after the workshop took place we held a final presentation at the school with the revised concepts and design. Attendees were several teachers, the head of school, some school-kids as well as colleagues and researchers from the university. All students showed their working interactive prototypes on the Smartboard. Each student presented his or her concept in four minutes sharp, followed by a two-minute open feedback round. As this was the very first public presentation for most of the class, this was also a great training for them. The feedback during the presentation was very constructive, positive and interesting. Feedback from the teachers was specially valuable for future developments and projects.

The very important last step in the design-class process and in the semester was the internal feedback round in class between the university teacher, the co-teacher, and the students. Here, the whole process and all the methods and steps were analyzed and the future use of those methods and value for the design process discussed.

DISCUSSION

The process throughout the semester was highly motivated and concentrated, and the outcomes very rich. It was a great pleasure to teach this class.

The group was diverse: not only was it a mixed student-group from different design disciplines (communication, product, and interface design), but their level of experience varied. For some of the students it was their first semester, and therefore their very first contact with design after high school. Some were in their second year of study and already had an idea of the design profession, others were going through an apprenticeship and were learning a related technical profession. The feedback from all those students (and also from the school) was throughout very positive. It was a novel approach to design for all of them, experienced or inexperienced. With respect to participatory design they were all beginners and therefore worked together beautifully. The class was evaluated via an anonymous questionnaire (17 participants) and an oral feedback round. Most students said the methods they learned were very valuable tools and they planned to keep using them in their further studies. Particularly, the testing was often mentioned as highly enlightening. Also the 'field-work' aspect – working with the 'real world' – was pointed out to be very inspiring, motivating and eye-opening.

More analysis is required to fully assess this class in terms of teaching methods to be able to build upon the lessons learned for future course development. The experiment to make a participatory 'fieldwork'-like design approach the subject-matter of a design basics class was very promising; it will be interesting and important though to observe the development of the participating design students to learn if taking this class will have an impact on their approach and understanding of the role of design in their future projects.

We look forward to future collaborations with the primary school and hope that some prototypes will turn into major design projects in the following semesters. After all, public education could be a huge and interesting field for designers, where design skills are greatly needed and very welcome. Sadly, due to the lack of public funds for the educational sector, this area is not yet of great interest to design firms and the like. However, as long as this is the case, we can always think of Victor Papanek and his invitation to designers to dedicate 10% of their working time and energy to non-profit social projects (Papanek 1971). Forty years later this is still a valid concept.

Figure 10. Final Presentation and Feedback Round in School-Classroom at 'Grundschule im Bornstedter Feld'.

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DESIGNING FROM GRANDMOTHERS DOMESTICITY IN BOGOTÁ

METHODOLOGIES AND PROCESSES

Carolina Agudelo
School of Design and Architecture, Universidad de los Andes
✉ aagudelo@uniandes.edu.co

ABSTRACT

The future cannot be understood without the past, without the traditions and without those tangible and intangible legacies that bind us emotionally to a place. In this lies the beauty that connects people with the objects that surround them and the spaces they live in.

From the study of the objects and the poetic and aesthetic aspects of grandmothers' houses in Bogotá, a proposal of both a location and various objects is developed. The proposal is an approach to a domesticity in which the role of gender and narratives of Manuel Carreño's traditional book *Manual de urbanidad y buenas maneras* (Manual of Civility and Good Manners) become the axis for creating this place of conversation between emotions, tradition and design.

KEY WORDS: *traditions, poetic descriptions, domesticity, customs, Bogotá*

INTRODUCTION

The places, their traditions and rituals contain codes, which make people connect emotionally with the tangible and intangible elements which are part of a culture. In this document a description is given of the observational methodologies that allowed us to map and evaluate the characteristics of grandmothers' houses in Bogotá. A study of the methodologies of identification of elements and their translation into a design language can also be found. Stories and interactions at the dinner table are analyzed to create an object and space proposal that poses a place where traditions and emotions materialize.

VISUAL ETHNOGRAPHY APPLIED TO THE SEARCH OF DESIGN CONCEPTS

This project started with the exploration of Bogotá houses, citizens, and what defines their domesticity. Various categories of houses to observe were established, within which the houses of Bogotá grandmothers were defined as objects of considerable study, as they are containers of memory, tradition and rituals that define important features to understand domesticity in Bogotá.

The starting point in the observation was a workshop in which a group of people, mostly art and design students, were asked to search in their family homes for a number of objects that reminded them of the emotional interactions of the houses' inhabitants with their respective spaces, objects, situations

and specific rituals. These aspects were established from an observation guide and compilation of information (Mosse, 2010). This guide allowed to gather aspects relating to the most special places in the houses, their spiritual centers, the more or less important objects, the main sources of light, people who lived there and their meeting centers, the newest and oldest objects in the houses, and the special rituals that take place there. From the observed aspects, a sensitive framework was created, to be able to recognize what it is that connects people with their houses, meaning that they are not just places that contain physical aspects related with design, materials, areas, etc., but that they also contain emotional aspects in the way they are inhabited and appropriated.

The compilation tool that was used is known as Visual Ethnography, employed by visual anthropology to obtain information through photography and video, on the manifestations of a culture "through its visible symbols embedded in gestures, ceremonies, rituals and artifacts located in built or natural environments" (Ruby, 1996).

1 The Soft Domesticity Workshop took place in Bogotá on February 2010. Carolina Agudelo, Coordinator of Textiles and Fashion area at Universidad de los Andes' Design Department, and Carole Collet, Deputy Director of the Textile Futures Research Centre of University of the Arts, London, directed it. The workshop's aims were to collect visual information of Bogotá homes and to explore the possibilities for textiles in a future scenario for Bogotá in 2050. Twenty people participated and approximately 60 houses/homes were explored and documented for the workshop.

Figure 1. Grandmothers home conceptual map/moodboard. Photography: Juanda Contreras + Daniel Pinilla. 2013.

Once the information was gathered, a map was organized based on the spaces that were repeated more often in the collected photographs. That was how the garden, the entrance, the lounge, the dining room, the kitchen, the inner courtyard, the hall, the rooms and other spaces were mapped. This map was denominated Moodboard, which, in the creation of a project, is used to develop concepts and allow the Creative Director and his team to understand the visual style that has to be achieved. A poetic description of each space, based on the information collected, gave way to the conceptualization process. This poetic descriptions are the base of the project's concept; they are linked with the story or feeling captured in the images. These images often relate to family background, particular events, different feelings, materials, people or places. Their highly emotional content can be an input to create stories, therefore creating a link between image and word.

CONCEPT PROTOTYPING TO ESTABLISH THE AESTHETICS OF A DESIGN PROJECT

The concept prototyping was built based on points of interest taken from the conceptual map of grandmothers' houses. This tool uses the previously developed aesthetic language to analyze and translate visual and conceptual information from new images. This construction is made from the designer's or creator's particular interest, in a synthesis and appropriation exercise. Therefore this tool is highly influenced by the creator's personal sensitivity and emotion as well as the project's specific needs. This methodology is used by trends development offices to establish the aesthetic precepts on which an industry will move years in advance.

Some points of interest were taken from the grandmothers' houses related to situations and rituals identified as repetitive from the information collected from interviews to the inhabitants of the homes observed during the workshop. Those situations and rituals were intended to be explored for the final purpose of the project.

The concepts developed from these points were:

- 1 *Spiritual Collector*: The faith and spiritual corners of grandmothers' houses in Bogotá. It has to do with the Catholic religion that most of the homes in Bogotá profess. Religion as a way of expressing spirituality.

Figure 2. Grandmothers home concepts prototyping. Photography: Luisa Rodríguez. 2010

- 2 *Glazed Tile with Sunday Flavor and Sunday Break*: The weekend meals prepared and set by the grandmother for her family. They become a meeting and behavioral ritual.
- 3 *Objects from a Withheld Past*: the most meaningful or antique objects that are, in their great majority, provided with stories and anecdotes.
- 4 *Rustic Silver Reflection*: Cabinets full of silver objects that play an important role in the materiality of Bogotá homes.
- 5 *Souvenirs of a Walked Road*: The small objects that contain stories or are themselves a story. Memories that remain hidden from the quotidian view in form of a secret.
- 6 *Cuddling Memories and Handmade Lifestyle*: Presence of fabrics and crochet as a work of grandmothers. Houses are wrapped in fabrics.

Amber Tableware: The tableware that is used only for guests and special events. It regularly came as a wedding gift from some European country and is visible but not reachable, as a sort of treasure.

SCENARIO BUILDING FROM A SPECIFIC NARRATIVE

For each one of the concepts a scenario visualization was made, that results from an exercise of collecting design models and doing several brainstorming sessions, in which keyword lists were developed concerning the interactions, compositions, materials, and narratives that the concepts express. Each of these scenarios was named and organized in an infographic for further analysis.

To continue the development of the project, the concept *Amber Tableware* was chosen because several of the answers in the questionnaires made during the visual ethnography situated the ritual around the table and the food, as one of the most important ones practiced in grandmothers' homes in Bogota.

This suggested a point of intersection between generations, the emotional connection provided by a meal; the table dressed and fine tableware are the points on which the ritual rotates.

The scenario built for this concept was established around the narrative about manners and behavior at the table and is guided by the book *Manual de urbanidad y buenas maneras* (Manual of Civility and Good Manners) of Manuel Carreño, published in the year 1853. Houses of grandmothers are the most traditional homes in urban Bogotá, becoming the last place where we can still find traditions and ways of behaving inherited from the nineteenth century. As a result of these influences, especially the English and the Victorian ones, the book traditionally known as *La urbanidad de Carreño* appeared in some South American countries (in the past part of the Gran Colombia, which included Venezuela, Colombia, Panama and Ecuador, some parts of Brazil, Perú and Nicaragua). The book was used in Colombia up until the 1970's, and was used as the guidebook to educate generations on how to behave in society. This traditional book was chosen for the development of the narrative of the scenario because it was a reference of good manners for many of Bogota's citizens. *La urbanidad de Carreño* has a chapter dedicated to behavior and etiquette at the table, from which the elements for the food ritual scenario development were extracted. The narrative of the scenario was named "The space of good manners, the objects of good customs".

These elements laid down the stage narrative into three phases: the table set up, the moment during the meal and the moment after the meal. An analysis was made in these three phases, about three elements that contain the insights on which the project's design phase was developed: the roles, the objects and the space. The roles established by Carreño were crucial to find out the relationships between the protagonists of the scenario and the elements of their story, for each of the project's pieces. For instance, the hostess, who is the lady of the house, is the reference point for the distribu-

Figure 3. Grandmothers home scenarios. Infographics: Jaime Patarroyo. 2012.

Figure 4. Amber china scenario / "The space of good manners, the objects of good customs". Infographic: Jaime Patarroyo. 2012.

Figure 5A. Table rituals infographic. Infographic: Lina Giraldo + Valentina Danna. 2012

Figure 5B. Objects, roles and spaces infographic. Infographic: Lina Giraldo + Valentina Danna. 2012

tion of the different dinner guests at a table according to their level of importance. Objects that are part of the ritual play an important role in the way the dinner is served, the use of the utensils and the appropriate limit in the gestures and behaviors at the table. The space defines the paths and interactions between one guest and another.

THE MATERIALIZATION OF THE SPACE OF GOOD MANNERS, THE OBJECTS OF GOOD CUSTOMS

From the infographics and the identified and declared elements, a design place was marked out. Therefore, it could be defined that a confined space (the floor) was needed, a central object for the ritual (the table), some objects in which the ritual's participants could be located (the chairs) and the elements to prepare the ritual and set up the table (the tableware).

Figure 6. Sketches and prototypes. Photography: Santiago Orjuela + Jaime Patarroyo. 2012

Figure 7. Space prototype and final lacy floor. Photography: Carolina Agudelo. 2012-2013

The Space

To be able to understand the space, a prototype was made to get a feel of the scale that the project's staging would finally have. With wooden boxes, the size of the space was established. It was already clear from an earlier sketching that a floor would limit the space. The floor was finally developed based on a piece of lace from the seventeenth century and ceramics were intervened and translated into a giant tablecloth. The lace is important within the materiality defined from the concept prototype. It is highly ornate, it denotes a woman's table and it forms part of the world of crochet and lace, found repeatedly in different scenarios of grandmothers' houses in Bogotá.

The Chairs

The design process and materialization of the chairs had to do with the people that would be seated on them and that, according to the ritual, are: the hostess or lady of the house, the gentleman of the house, the important couple of guests, and the not so important couple of guests. In this way the search for the chairs started. They would translate the social features and behavior from those who were going to seat at the table depending on their degree of importance. The process of sketching was done with the chairs to emphasize features and characteristics of the table's characters. The chairs of the host and hostess or gentleman and lady of the house have a common gesture: they are long and squared. The gentleman's has a heavy gesture whereas the lady's one is much lighter.

Figure 8A. Lady's chair. Photography: Juanda Contreras. 2013.

The chairs of the important guests are rounded and decorated on top with an ornate carving. The chairs were joined in a gesture that determines the dominance of men over women at the stage of defining the positions in the table and other aspects of their lives⁹.

The chairs of the non important guests are simpler, also rounded but with less ornaments. They were also joined with the same gesture of men over women. The chair is uncomfortable, showing the hostess' indifference for the guests' comfort, it has the seat tilted forward pushing the guest onto the table and forcing him to use his legs for support.

Figure 8B. Gentleman's chair. Photography: Juanda Contreras. 2013.

- 2 For some people the book *La urbanidad de Carreño* appears at times extremely sexist and controlling in reference to women's activities and gestures. Considering it was written in 1850, it is understood that women's freedom was restricted by male figures, father or husband.

Figure 9. Important guests' chair. Photography: Juanda Contreras. 2013.

Figure 10. Unimportant guests' chair. Photography: Juanda Contreras. 2013.

Figure 11. Table. Photography: Juanda Contreras. 2013.

Figure 12. Tableware. Photography: Juanda Contreras. 2013.

The Table

The table was a fortunate discovery. In the quest for a piece that would fit the size of the originally developed prototype, it was found in a warehouse in a city near Bogotá. The table was not intervened or modified. It was finished and painted and presented that way.

The Tableware

In the same way as the chairs, each set of the tableware was developed taking into account the characteristics of the guests and the narrative imposed on each one of them.

For the prototype, paper traditional lace table covers were used, that were part of the materiality of the constructed scenario. White standard tableware was used as the base, and for the design, instructions from La Urbanidad de Carreño were taken, and thus, the borders were ornamented so that the food would not touch them, precise instructions for the use of the cutlery and where it should rest after eating were written, a tilted soup bowl was made and plates were made as baskets where only one loaf of bread would fit. From these prototypes, the ceramic dishes were made, taking paper lace onto different materials distant from flexibility, that despite being heavy and rigid, achieved a feeling of lightness.

The Space of Good Manners, the Objects of Good Customs: Installation Artwork

Figure 13A. Installation. Photography: Juanda Contreras. 2013.

COMPILATION OF METHODOLOGIES

Some methodologies related to fields as design, arts and social sciences were applied through the development of the project.

Visual ethnography was used to obtain first hand information about homes in Bogotá and their domesticity. From all the images collected that contained sensible and emotional information it was possible to build visual maps that are known as moodboards. A moodboard is a tool use by designers to communicate their ideas effectively through the development of a project. Conceptual maps, that in this project are the conceptual conclusion of moodboards, were built from the answers obtained from the questionnaires done during the visual ethnography. Those answers related with sensations of the images selected conclude in phrases used to name them.

Concept prototyping is the appropriation of aesthetic concepts to be reinterpreted and presented from the particular interest of the project. All those images constructed become the starting point from which different design scenarios were built. The scenario building was made from the insights, referents and narratives compiled to communicate the concept values effectively. To visualize the conclusions of the scenarios, infographics were developed as a visual conclusion to establish the most important and definite ideas in the development of the project

The construction of narratives around the concepts was a crucial task for the project. Through stories it was possible to design around poetry, relating it to recover traditions and the way people will relate to them in the future. There was emotional information that was fundamental to the narrative behind the pieces and the space. From narratives and scenarios it was possible to make sketches and fast prototypes to materialize ideas. Forms, sizes, colors, textures, materials and interactions were established and evaluated to decide what pieces to develop for the project. Material experimentation was fundamental to be able to push the materials forward and is made through an animated conversation within materials at laboratories and workshops with crafters involved. In this project the rigid materials become softer in appearances because of those conversations.

Figure 13B. Installation. Photography: Carolina Agudelo. 2013.

The definition of materials and the making of final prototypes are the final phase of the project, giving an accurate idea of what was explored and the decisions made in each one of the phases developed.

CONCLUSIONS

This project begins with a sensitive and emotional journey to the places where we live as citizens of Bogotá, places that contain traditions and rituals passed down from generation to generation, and aesthetic codes that make us feel at home.

One of the main objectives of the project is to create a map of the tools and methodologies that we use as designers and artists in creation processes. Those methodologies we use in decision-making that are carried out in a sensitive way, but that also correspond to the tangible needs of a project, such as choosing a color or material. Many of these tools, taken from sciences and social sciences, translated to a sensitive perspective, make creation in design and art an interesting place where rationality and emotion converge.

This project celebrates the development of objects that spin a story of meanings surrounding the ritual of food. It is based on a book of manners that, although currently out of date, contains information on our culture and permits us to connect with a past that gives us inputs to define our present and future materiality, in a celebration of local customs we can project to the world.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

“The Space of Good Manners, the Objects of Good Customs” was a research project developed under the FAPA (APSF Assistant Professor Support Fund) at the Design Department of Universidad de los Andes, Bogotá. I would like to thank Lucía Tejeiro and Catalina Manotas for their help in copyediting and translating this document. Thanks to all our grandmothers because through them we are connected with traditions and good manners.

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»CO-PHOTOGRAPHY« AS A RESEARCH TOOL – USING NARRATIVE PHOTOGRAPHY AS A PARTICIPATORY TOOL FOR USER INSIGHTS

Annelie Franke

Universidad de los Andes

✉ afranke@uniandes.edu.co

Monika Hoinkis

University of Applied Sciences Potsdam

✉ hoinkis@fh-potsdam.de

WORKSHOP POSITION PAPER

Background Issues

As a contribution to this year's conference theme *Colours of Care* we propose a workshop on *Co-photography* as a design research tool. The term *Co-photography* was coined by the workshop's organizers to combine participatory methods as applied in co-design processes and photography as an

empiric story-telling tool. The workshop is linked to the D&E 2014 design case paper "*Tap Anything.*" *A Design (Class) Case: Teaching Participatory Design Methods as Design Basics.* The design case reports from a participatory design process including a workshop from which the idea of *Co-photography* evolved (see Fig. 1).

We see the workshop located within the designated conference topics *Design for Social Innovation, Methodological Issues of Design and Emotion* and *Experience and Interaction.*

Figure 1. Scene from participatory workshop in a primary school. Playful and effective rating system for kids 'jury' rating prototypes using cardboard plates with smiley faces.

In this hands-on workshop participants will learn about participatory methods in general, about the potential and creative value in developing their own participatory methods and tools for user insights, and will then go out into the field and practice *Co-photography* within a one-hour brief project based on their own method design. The workshop results in a popup exhibition of the photographic results.

Co-design describes involving stakeholders and future users of products or services strongly in the design process. Expressing creativity, ideas and thoughts in words or sketches may be difficult for many people if they are not used or trained to do so. A common method to help them express themselves and to be creative is providing participatory toolkits (Sanders 2003, 2013): kits containing crafting material such as stickers, Lego blocs, fabrics, etc. as a means of assembling prototypes and sketch ideas.

Our workshop is based on Liz Sanders model of *Say, Do, Make* – listing tools and techniques that complement and reinforce each other in the participatory design process (2013). We apply this model to photography as a means of expressing oneself and tell a story. Photography in general is an excellent medium to capture emotions and information, therefore it is an essential documentary tool for later analysis in participatory workshops, observations, etc. We propose not using photography to document a participatory outcome in a co-design workshop but to let it be the outcome: materials from a toolkit provided by the researchers shall be used by the questioners for making artifacts, props, etc. to ‘stage’ their photographic answer (see Fig. 2). The outcome could be described as a visual short story (see ‘Narrative Photography,’ e.g. Black Box Gallery 2011).

This technique draws from the concept of design probes (Gaver 1999), in which it is not the researcher who takes photos as a tool for insight, as known from the visual data collection in ethnographic photography and visual anthropology (e.g. Theye 1989, Levi-Strauss 1978, Sander 1929), but the future user/questioner who is asked to take a photo as a visual answer to a question.

Workshop Goal

Attendees get an overview of participatory approaches and methods and learn that methods can be varied, changed,

adapted – they can themselves be designed. They make their own hands-on experiences with photography as a participatory method, preparing interviews, approaching questioners, collecting data, etc. Analysis of the data will be brushed but not executed in depth. The workshop is meant to enhance the vocabulary of design researchers that already use participatory methods but have not yet included photography to their palette, as well as designers and researchers that are entirely unfamiliar with the co-design method and would like to practice it for the first time in a playful environment.

Approach

Part 1 (30 minutes): brief keynote presentations by the organizers on the use of participatory methods and applications in the design context as well as a brief introduction to narrative photography

Part 2 (30 minutes): pressure project. Design brief, brainstorming, developing individual method, paper prototyping, fieldwork preparation

Part 3 (60 minutes): fieldwork/practice *Co-photography*. Attendees swarm out and get people to take photos as answers to prepared simple but playful questions (e.g., ‘How are you today?’, ‘How was your lunch today?’ and also more complex questions like ‘What is your relationship to your neighbors?’, ‘What is your relationship to politics?’, etc.)

Part 4 (60 minutes): sighting and selection of images, open discussion, résumé

Part 5 (post-workshop, optional): printing out photos on site on a mobile printer provided by the workshop’s organizers for putting together a pop-up exhibition of workshop results (photos) at the D&E conference

NAMES, AFFILIATIONS, AND CONTACT INFORMATION OF THE ORGANIZERS:

Prof. Monika Hoinkis (contact person), University of Applied Sciences Potsdam
Email: hoinkis@fh-potsdam.de

Prof. Annelie Franke, Universidad de los Andes
Email: afranke@uniandes.edu.co

Fig. 2: Based on Sanders (2013) model of *Say, Do and Make* – tools and techniques that complement and reinforce each other in the participatory design process. Model showing *Co-photography* involving all dimensions of a participatory design toolkit

Intended Number of Attendees: Minimum: 12, maximum: 25

Planned Length of the Workshop: Half a day workshop (3 hours)

Preferred City for the Workshop: Bogotá

Characteristics of the Space/room Needed to Conduct the Workshop:

Workshop room with tables and chairs for max. 25 participants, projector, flipchart.

Optional: exhibition space during the conference. A designated wall or small room, ideally in a waiting/resting area. If no wall is available, partition walls or similar.

Materials needed by attendees: digital camera, if on hand: laptop.

Basic materials for toolkits are provided by workshop organizers. Attendees are encouraged to contribute by bringing whatever material they have at hand.

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Annelie Franke is a designer and photographer born in 1976 in Lauchhammer, Germany. Between 1997 and 2001 she studied Communication Design at the Rhein Main University in Wiesbaden (Germany). From 2001 to 2004 she studied Visual Communication at the University of the Arts Berlin (UdK).

She has received design and photography awards and worked as a designer with various agencies and educational institutions in Berlin, Weimar, Schwerin and Wiesbaden. In 2006 she followed her heart to Bogotá and began working as a professor at the Universidad de los Andes in the Department of Architecture and Design. Her emphases are digital studio photography, experimental typography, conceptual and information design. Besides, she works as freelance designer and photographer in various projects in both countries. Her artistic work stresses the importance of small things in life. Using various media such as photography, illustration and design, she exalts unnoticed and common things of everyday life to turn them into main actors of her work, and ennobles evident ugliness to natural beauty.

www.anneliefranke.de

Monika Hoinkis, born 1978 in Hanover, Germany is a Berlin-based designer and design educator. She studied visual communication and time based art in Berlin and Sydney, Australia, graduating from University of the Arts Berlin (UdK). Currently she holds a professorship for processual design at University of Applied Sciences in Potsdam. When she finds the time Monika also works on private art and design projects as well as design commissions as a freelance designer. Her work was internationally exhibited and received diverse awards (iF, tdc, ADC, reddot). Her particular interest lies in the social and societal impacts and implications of design.

www.monikahoinkis.de

PRODUCT IMPACT TOOL WORKSHOP

MASTERING AFFECT AND EFFECT IN HUMAN-PRODUCT RELATIONS

Steven Dorrestijn & Wouter Eggink (corresponding author)
University of Twente, Industrial Design Engineering, Faculty of Engineering Technology
✉ s.dorrestijn@utwente.nl, w.eggink@utwente.nl

KEYWORDS: *Product Impact Tool; Influence of Behavior; Social Engagement in Design; Shaping Technology; Philosophy of Technology*

INTRODUCTION

The Product Impact Tool is the application-oriented result of the research project Product Impact on User Behavior, aiming to investigate the impact of technology on users and to make the insights applicable in the design process (Dorrestijn 2012). The impact of technology on users and society is an important topic in research on technology in reflexive research fields (philosophy of technology, media studies). Especially in recent empirically oriented philosophy of technology and the related interdisciplinary field of Science and Technology Studies this has resulted in concepts that promise to be of interest for application in design as well. For example, the notions of script and of delegation of action from humans to technologies (Latour 1992) may be compared to research at the interface of psychology and design on affordances (Norman 1988), persuasive technology (Fogg 2003), and nudges (Thaler & Sunstein 2008).

Design practice has made little use of this knowledge, although to date there is a growing awareness of the possible advantages of combining research fields (Tromp, Hekkert & Verbeek 2011); the recombination of perspectives is promising for understanding human-technology interaction. This is useful for improving product usability as well as for addressing ethical issues in product design (Lilley 2009; Lockton 2010; Dorrestijn & Verbeek 2013). It can also provide guidance for the shaping of new technology (Eggink 2013). The Product Impact Tool aims to translate theories about the influence of technology

on design practice. The tool comprises a model and a format for a session that provides instructions on employment of the model. The workshop will provide an extensive introduction to the model, and workshop participants will then be guided through a session to apply the tool to a case (social engagement in neighborhoods).

MODEL: MODES OF AFFECT AND TYPES OF EFFECT

As part of the tool the product impact model serves to structure the exploration of user guiding and changing effects. The product impact model shows a human being, affected by technology from different sides. The model comprises a repertoire of different types of effects of technology on humans, ordered according to four different modes of interaction.

This model reflects an analysis of human-technology relations based mainly on work in phenomenological philosophy and media studies (Flusser 1999; Ihde 1990; McLuhan 2003). It is however equally possible to use the model without much reference to these background theories. The interaction modes can also be described in a more design- and exact science oriented vocabulary. Thus, the relationships and interactions between humans and technology are categorized as follows: before-the-eye, to-the-hand, behind-the-back, and above-the-head (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Product Impact Model

Before-the-eye (cognitive)

The most common understanding of using technology is probably that humans employ technologies as means for reaching their goals more effectively. Technology can contribute to such goal-oriented action by supporting and directing the cognitive processes of decision-making. The first type of influence in the quadrant before-the-eye is “guidance” towards intended use. In design this effect is applied by aiming for self-evident forms and colors, by adding arrows and text, etc. The influence on human action can also be more intrusive: “persuasion” through design. In this case technology not just guides towards proper use but intends to change people’s behavior, as in the case of pop-up banners on websites. In either case technology addresses the human decision making process.

To-the-hand (physical)

Technical products can also shortcut cognition and push or subtly guide the user’s body and gestures. Although to have products before-the-eye may be the most common understanding, having products to-the-hand is the more basic interaction with technology. To-the-hand, or physical interaction is about holding handles, pushing buttons, the height and comfort of chairs and desks, or the hard safety measurements of locks, helmets, fences and the like.

Behind-the-back (environment)

Apart from influences that reach humans through direct contact, technology can also influence people in an indirect way. The material-technical environment and the infrastructure form a background that facilitates or directs human action and

history. It is generally not possible to redesign a whole product environment, but the success or failure of the appropriation of products can be understood and influenced by addressing the environmental effects.

Above-the-head (abstract)

The interaction modes “physical”, “cognitive”, and “environment” are all about concrete relations between humans and technologies. This means that there are always concrete cases and examples at the base of the analysis. In the “above-the-head quadrant”, in contrast, an abstract theoretical approach looks at the relations between humans and technologies in general. What is the nature, or the essence, of technology? What is the meaning of human freedom or privacy in the light of the impacts of technology? Grasping the interdependency of technology and society at this general level remains speculative; at least, opinions are very diverse and often contradictory. The philosophical views of technology vary from “utopian technology” to “dystopian technology”, with “ambivalent hybridity” as the contemporary synthesis in the middle. Obviously, it is not in the power of neither designers, nor users to change how technology influences humans throughout history and on a worldwide scale. Still, these generalized understandings determine visions of technology that help to understand ethical controversies and people’s attitudes to technology.

WORKSHOP DESCRIPTION

The Product Impact Tool workshop is designed to raise the participants’ awareness of the possibilities they have for influencing peoples’ behavior through product design. As the tool is both meant for analysing product impact and for design support, these two functions will be addressed. The participants will practice with the tool in groups of three and they will work with powerpoint-templates, as we want to record the results of the workshop for our research. The workshop follows a half-day schedule, with hands-on experience in two rounds. After the introduction, the participants will become familiar with the product impact tool in an analysis exercise. In the second round they will practice with a design case. Both rounds are structured in several sub-assignments.

Design case

In a design exercise, participants perform a short design assignment in several steps. The case is derived from our own research practice about the influence of technology on social engagement. One example is the application of FaceTime to stimulate contact between neighbors of different ages in a Dutch village called Lepelstraat (Jeugdjournaal 2013). But one can also think of the arrangement of a local park area which encourages people to come out and do sports or exercises together (van der Meer 2013). In the workshop the participants are going to conceive product or service concepts that (can) influence people to live more healthily at a neighborhood level. The participants may choose from three different

sub-themes that are particularly suitable to touch on all the aspects of the Product Impact Tool: stimulate healthy eating together; gardening and/or growing your own supplies; moving or exercising to be fit.

The design results will be discussed and shared with all the participants. To make this an interesting session and speed up the exchange of insights, we do this by interviewing the designers. All materials from the workshop, as well as the literature and presentations will be available through our website.

See also: <http://www.stevendorrestijn.nl/tool/>
<http://www.utwente.nl/gw/wijsb/organization/dorrestijn/>
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Steven Dorrestijn

Dr. Steven Dorrestijn is senior lecturer/researcher in ethics and technology at Saxion University of Applied Sciences, the Netherlands. In his research Dorrestijn contrived a model of effects of technologies on people, and also focused on people's practices when accommodating new technologies in their lives. This perspective on the role of technologies in people's everyday practices is a much-needed complement to both the theoretical approaches in ethics and the practical approaches in user-centred design.

Wouter Eggink

Dr. Ir. Wouter Eggink is a design professional and assistant professor at the University of Twente, especially interested in the relationships between design, technology, and society. He teaches this subject at the Bachelor and Master programme of Industrial Design Engineering. In his research Eggink approaches human-technology relations both from a Design History perspective and through Design for the Future, supported by Scenario Planning. He has also published extensively on Design Education, and on enhancing Creativity in design through the well-considered application of Visual Essays.

HUMAN INTUITION WHEN DESIGNING FOR EMOTIONS: HOW THE DESIGNER'S PERSONAL BACKGROUND CAN HELP (OR RUIN) A PROJECT

Leandro Miletto Tonetto

Universidade do Vale do Rio dos Sinos (Unisinos) and Zooma – Consumer Experience

✉ ltonetto@gmail.com, leandro@zooma.com.br

ABSTRACT

Emotional design usually refers to designing in order to evoke or prevent particular emotions among users. This workshop is not aimed at discussing solely users' emotions, it is also focused on understanding how the designer's emotional experience might influence his/her work. Emotion and reasoning are not antonyms. Emotion can even help us to make better decisions, e.g., working as an adaptive sign of danger, when basic survival needs are threatened. In the tradition of cognitive research on decision-making, emotions can play an informational role, filling in the lack of information that people sometimes find when they need to make decisions. It is a heuristic mechanism, which is understood, in the cognitive sciences, as intuitive, since intuition is strongly based on emotion. Professionals in a variety of fields, such as design, medicine and law, might need to evaluate diverse situations and make quick decisions, grounded on impressions built in a few seconds of observation. These impressions have an emotional basis and are commonly based on personal and professional previous experiences, which are part of the mentioned heuristic process. The lack of information that would allow designers to logically analyse the problem is filled in with affective content. This way, the workshop goal is to facilitate designers to understand how their intuitive thinking can help (or ruin) their design.

KEYWORDS: *design for emotions; intuition; rationality; design process*

INTRODUCTION: BACKGROUND ISSUES

Emotional design usually refers to designing in order to evoke or prevent particular emotions. Desmet (2009) described four approaches to design for emotions: (a) the user-based approach has the users' emotions as foundations of the design and usually includes them in the design process; (b) in the designer-based perspective, professionals aim at challenging users with innovative artefacts; (c) using the theory-based approach, professionals search insights in theory to feed the process, while (d) the research-based perspective is grounded on user research.

When designers are not based on user research, they might be led to ignore that their experience does not necessarily represent that of the target group, since emotional experience is commonly understood as triggered by stimuli that might change among distinct types of user/person (Frijda, 1986). This means that the same stimulus, such as the sound of rain, can

trigger relaxation among those who enjoy water, or even fear, e.g., if it is heard by a community that has been through some kind of natural disaster related to water. Thus, it is possible that designers, trusting on their views on how to trigger a certain emotion, could design biased solutions to simple problems.

This workshop is not aimed at discussing solely users' emotions, but it is also focused on understanding how the designer's emotional experience might influence their work. Emotion and reasoning are not antonyms. Emotion can even help us to make better decisions, e.g., working as an adaptive sign of danger, when basic survival needs are threatened. In the tradition of cognitive research on decision-making (Tversky and Kahneman, 1974), Kahneman (2003) states that emotions can play an informational role, filling in the lack of information that people sometimes find when they need to make decisions. It is a heuristic mechanism, which is understood, in the cognitive sciences, as intuitive, since intuition is strongly based on emotion. Professionals in a variety of fields, such as design,

medicine and law, might need to evaluate diverse situations and make quick decisions, grounded on impressions built in a few seconds of observation. These impressions have an emotional basis and are commonly based on personal and professional previous experiences, which are part of the mentioned heuristic process. The lack of information that would allow designers to logically analyse the problem is filled in with affective content.

One of the most common theoretical perspectives in the Design and Emotion field is the Appraisal Theory. It matches perfectly Kahneman and Tversky's (1974, reviewed by Kahneman, 2003) perspective on intuition, since they are both originated in cognitive psychology. In the Appraisal Theory, emotions are understood as the result of a user's appraisal of products, services or any other stimulus (Frijda, 1986; Demir, Desmet, Hekkert, 2009). How does this product relate to my well being? If the answer reveals expected or real benefits, a positive emotion is likely to occur (e.g., joy, happiness). If it is negative, a negative emotion might be the outcome (e.g., sadness).

Also, users' concerns might influence the emotional outcomes of people's interaction with products and services. Concerns are a person's goals, motives, or any other sensitivity (Frijda, 1986), such as being safe or have healthy food on a daily basis. By understanding users concerns and how consumers appraise products and services, it is possible to understand what triggers these emotions, and to evoke them through design. It states a connection between causes (design elements) and effects (emotional impact of design).

The mentioned guidelines refer to a variety of possibilities. They range from very concrete information to abstract properties of a product. As examples, it is possible to mention the use of marble in home projects (concrete information), if it is a trigger for sophistication to a specific type of user (in projects that aim at evoking this experience), and to design of a device to help older people to achieve everyday goals (abstract), instead of solving the problem for them (if "do it yourself" is a common trigger to pride in this target group), in a project to stimulate pride among the elder. These examples reinforce the idea that emotion has an individual basis and that distinct kinds of users might appraise similar situations in very distinct ways, which means that what triggers the same emotions might change from one target group to another.

Thus, being intuitive can be particularly dangerous to beginners and/or professionals with a lack of knowledge about the target group, since intuition will work based on the information and impressions they already have. On the other hand, knowing how intuition works can be a great tool, when used consciously. It allows us to be creative without overestimating our knowledge about the target group. This way, intuition is best employed when practiced.

WORKSHOP GOAL AND APPROACH

The workshop goal is to facilitate designers to understand how their intuitive thinking can help (or ruin) their design. Through

an exercise described below, they will be trained to understand how their intuition works, facilitating self-knowledge, and their intuitive solutions will be confronted with user research. In order to achieve this goal, the workshop will have five moments:

- a) Short design task (75 min): A design task will be based on Demir, Ozkaramanli and Desmet (2010) experiences. Emotion formulas will be built by the design team, including the definition of a product to be designed for a low-income Brazilian group¹, as well as a discussion about the emotion (pride) to be stimulated among them. After that, a concern analysis will be developed, followed by the formulation of design concepts and their presentation to the group.
- b) Projection of a film about the target group (10 min): A short documentary on pride, filmed in this low-income Brazilian community, will be shown to the design team. It shows people's testimonial on events that made them proud of something or somebody.
- c) Mini lecture on Intuition (20 min): The lecture will be given by the workshop facilitator (and author of this proposal), and will cover the main topic "How (design) intuition works", following the model described in the introduction.
- d) Analysis on how the design team would change (or not) their design after watching the film (45 min): Participants will be asked to evaluate the actual potential of their design to evoke the intended emotion (pride) and, if needed, adjust and/or criticise their design.
- e) Facilitator's analysis on the design team's intuitive thinking (30 min): In order to stimulate self-knowledge, the workshop facilitator will finish the activities by analysing participants' design decisions, showing how intuition affected their design in good and/or bad directions, which means, helping to achieve the design aim or doing the opposite.

INTENDED NUMBER OF ATTENDEES

Maximum: 30; Minimum: 12

DURATION OF THE WORKSHOP

Half-day (3 hours)

THE PREFERRED CITY FOR THE WORKSHOP

Bogotá

¹ The group of freelance cleaners was defined to set a target with characteristics potentially distinct from the design team.

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SPACE/ROOM NEEDED TO CONDUCT THE WORKSHOP

Chairs and table to develop work in groups.

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SUBTHEME 4 Well-being and Sustainability

Preservation of positive social, economic, psychological and medical states.

Includes these topics:

- Design & Well-Being (incl. food, healthcare & love)
- Sustainable Lifestyle
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THE BELGIAN RESIDENTIAL CARE LANDSCAPE: A STUDY OF ARCHITECTURAL CARE CONCEPTS THROUGH THE LENS OF SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING

Ruth Stevens, Ann Petermans, Jan Vanrie
Faculty of Architecture and arts, Hasselt University, Diepenbeek, Belgium
✉ ruth.stevens@uhasselt.be, ann.petermans@uhasselt.be, jan.vanrie@uhasselt.be

ABSTRACT

Subjective well-being (SWB) is an emerging research topic in the field of design sciences in general, and in the field of (interior) architecture in particular. However, research that focuses on the question of how (interior) architecture can positively contribute to SWB is still in its infancy. Taking into account the increasing greyness of our population, design for SWB in the field of residential care design seems very valuable. Therefore, this paper gives a first SWB-exploration of the Belgian intramural residential care landscape. The two most common intramural care concepts in Belgium will be analyzed through the lens of Desmet and Pohlmeier's (2013) Positive Design Framework by looking at the first author's ethnographic research data, which resulted from volunteer work. The results give insight into which of the existing concepts has the most SWB-potential while taking into account elderly persons' changing demands relating to positive experiences in living environments.

KEYWORDS: *subjective well-being, interior architecture, residential care typology, elderly people*

INTRODUCTION

Subjective well-being (SWB) is gaining attention in academic research (e.g. Duyarappah, 2010; Desmet & Pohlmeier 2013). In literature, SWB has several general definitions, but the ones by Diener (1999) and Lyubomirsky (2007) are the most relevant for our research. Specifically within the field of architecture and interior architecture, interest in and attention to design for SWB is emerging. Currently, the architectural type most closely linked to issues related to SWB in Belgium is that of residential care for the elderly. We use the term 'residential care' for the mix of different types of permanent stay for elderly persons, that also provide some form of (medical) care and assistance. In this sector, the architectural concept and the type of care provision are inextricably connected. Due to the ageing population, this sector is under pressure, evidenced by the threat of shortage in vacancies (Vlaams Agentschap Zorg en Gezondheid, 2012, 2013). However, equally problematic is the negative connotation residential care has in today's public discourse. This seems to be caused partially by the negative image with regards to the living experiences in the

architectural environment of these settings, which are often perceived as 'rather clinical': several studies and public complaints of residents mark this problem area (Callewaert & De Maeseneer, 2000; Neos, 2013; Penninx et al., 2007; Stichting SBO-NH, 2011; Vlaamse Ouderenraad, 2012; Ministerie van Volkshuisvesting NL, 2010). The interactions between a person and his/her physical environment reveal an interaction between objective well-being (OWB), or the realization of 'primary needs', such as shelter, hygiene, nourishment, and usability in the physical environment which are inherent in this setting, and subjective well-being (SWB), that is an intuitive/emotional 'state of mind'; a personal status, which is gaining importance but apparently does not seem to be provided by these settings. In other words, the new demand for positive (living) experiences in the physical environment exceeds what the presently built environment of the archetypical 'old peoples' home' as a 'resting place' for the elderly, seems to offer. The accomplishment of OWB does not seem to suffice for the flourishing of elderly people in residential care (e.g., Miller et al., 2012). This problem has an architectural undertone. In our view, this implies that a possible key to obtaining SWB in these environments can be found in the quality of the architectural

design and that (interior) architects are challenged to incorporate this intriguing relationship between a person and his/her physical environment in residential care.

This paper is a first step in a research program with the purpose of augmenting SWB in residential care for the elderly through manipulating the (interior) architectural design. When looking at the history of the design focus in residential care architecture (see Stevens et al., 2013) we notice that the introduction of OWB-research topics in the architectural design process in the 1970s (e.g. Universal Design, accessibility, ergonomics) had a great impact on architectural realizations (Mens & Wagenaar, 2009). The interiors of residential care became more adapted to what people needed: user friendliness for elderly who became more and more physically challenged, etc. In other words, this OWB-research contributed to shaping the environment to the needs and demands of people towards their physical environment. Currently, a similar activity is initiated concerning the research topic of SWB, or the newly posed wishes elderly persons have concerning their habitat (Stichting SBO-NH, 2011; Vlaamse Ouderenraad, 2012). However, today we are not ready to provide sufficient design information to (interior) architects in order for them to integrate SWB in their creative processes, since there are still many unanswered questions regarding what SWB actually means for the elderly in their built environment. For OWB, on the other hand, a firm knowledge base has already been established, and although there is still considerable work to be done, the transfer of this knowledge to designers has also been executed, as evidenced by the many faces and the variety of concepts of residential care present today. Indeed, when we randomly look at the architectural realization of residential care settings in Belgium, we immediately notice a number of care concepts that differ in the sort of care delivery, the specific target group of residents (level of dependence/independence, age, generational differences), etc. Although all care concepts today largely comply with OWB-demands of the target group, it is far less clear how these different concepts perform with regards to SWB. From a typological point-of-view, it is therefore an interesting starting-point to systematically list these variations of OWB-certified residential care concepts, and evaluate them from the perspective of SWB.

RESEARCH PURPOSE

The main objective in this paper is to get insight into how Belgian residential care concepts currently stand in relation to SWB. First, we give a classified typological overview of the Belgian residential care landscape to frame our research (see Figure 1). We then focus on the specific residential care type of intramural care for a SWB analysis. The focus on the intramural care type evolved out of bringing the entire typological classification in contact with the current care need/situation in Belgium. Statistics show that 2.3% of the Belgian population is in need of long term assistance and care on a constant basis (Statistics Belgium, 2014). Out of the people aged 80 or older, already 42% reside in long-term residential care, and can be defined as the target group of the intramural care type. Even though the government has been investing in and building a great deal of these intramural care facilities over the last decade, and already a great number of Belgian elderly reside in these facilities, a climax has currently been reached relating to a shortage in vacancies.

To continue, the intramural care type will be analyzed based on its objective characteristics. Afterwards, we try to get insight into how intramural care in Belgium currently stands in relation to SWB by analyzing this type through the lens of Desmet and Pohlmeier's 'Positive Design Framework' (2013).

THE BELGIAN RESIDENTIAL CARE TYPOLOGY AND THE ARCHITECTURAL CARE CONCEPTS

In order to get an overview of the residential care landscape in Belgium to frame our research, we listed the nationally acknowledged and government granted types (Evrard, 2013; Koning Boudewijnstichting, 2014; Myncke et al., 2007; Neos, 2014; Vlaamse Ouderenraad, 2013; Plus Magazine Knack, 2014; San Egidio, 2014; Swinnen, 2012; Vlaams Agentschap zorg en gezondheid, 2014; Waals Gewest Portaal, 2014) and clustered them through a user-centered approach, which resulted in a classification into three major types: (i) ageing in place; (ii) assisted living; and (iii) intramural care. This typology is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: A typology of the Belgian residential care landscape.

THE BELGIAN INTRAMURAL CARE TYPE

In this section we define the type of intramural care and elaborate on the objective characteristics of the two most important architectural care concepts within this type.

Definition

The intramural care type unites elderly care concepts that imply a permanent stay for a specific target group of elderly people who are highly dependent on help with activities of daily living (ADL) and care provision (Vlaams agentschap voor zorg en gezondheid, 2014), and have severe physical and/or lucidity problems. The architectural care concepts in this type offer the same amount of care and assistance. Also, these concepts must offer certain indoor services, such as physiotherapy and daytime animation. There are two intramural care concepts mentioned in Figure 1; i.e., the residential care center (RCC) and the small-scale living concept, that differ with regards to the scale of the projects and the attention for the creation of a homelike atmosphere.

Objective characteristics

In this section, we zoom in on the intramural care type and analyze the objective characteristics of its architectural concepts. Intramural care has two government-granted architectural concepts in the Belgian landscape (see Figure 1): the residential care center (RCC), and the small-scale living concept. Although they both appeal to the same target group, they have a very different general approach. A first difference can be found in their occurrence and initiation. Small-scale living facilities are less widely spread than the RCC, which can be found in almost every municipality in Belgium (Vlaams agentschap Zorg en Gezondheid, 2014; Waals Portaal, 2014). To give an idea, there are approximately 1620 RCCs, versus only a few dozen small-scale living facilities. This demonstrates that the RCC is more available to Belgian elderly persons. A reason for this occurrence seems to be that the RCC was the top elderly residential care concept promoted by the Belgian government after the ‘International year of the Elderly’, that was organized in 1999 by the United Nations (Callewaert & De Maeseneer, 2000). The realization of these facilities has therefore been heavily subsidized. Small-scale facilities on the other hand, are a relatively recent concept that originate in private initiatives or non-profit organizations (e.g., San Egidio Simeon en Hanna, 2014). The Belgian governments have only recently started to express interest in this type of intramural care, and have therefore not yet formed legislation for this type to comply with, or a subsidization scheme. Without governmental financial support, these facilities are quite expensive to build, but foremost also more expensive to live in for the residents.

The most important differentiation from our point-of-view, however, must be made concerning the living experience of the residents, implied in SWB. Small scale living facilities try to be experienced and perceived as very close to a natural home setting, atmosphere, and living experience, which is evidenced by the architectural layout of a typical family house and in the

concerned personnel management. These facilities provide care for a moderate number of elderly persons that reside together in one house (e.g., San Egidio Simeon en Hanna, 2014; Koning Boudewijnstichting, 2009). There are no nurses in clinical outfits that reveal their actual duty, but nurses who take the role of ‘housekeeper’, dressing like an ordinary person, taking care of lunch and dinner, entertaining the residents, but who also fulfill the necessary medical tasks (Wetzels, 2013). RCCs on the other hand are usually built up from several wards in which the elderly live together in larger numbers following strict daily schedules. They also have a strict day and nighttime regime: daytime is spent in the communal spaces (e.g., dining room, cafeteria, recreation room), and nighttime in the private (bed)room of the resident. In small-scale living facilities, however, the ‘communal spaces’ are very similar to rooms present in almost every single-family house: the kitchen, the living room, etc., in which residents can stay when they want to.

Combining this information, we notice that from the viewpoint of a future resident, amongst the two options to choose from, one is a small scale facility, which has a high chance of not being located in one’s direct living area, and is a financial uncertainty, since subsidization is not guaranteed. The other option is the RCC, which one will probably find in one’s proper town/municipality, but which generally has a negative connotation concerning living experiences in a way that not many people make the choice to live there voluntarily or based on positive living expectations (Vanden Boer et al., 2006). In most cases this situation will lead to a selection process by default in favor of the RCC. The already very limited choice is usually nullified by more practical reasons like distance from the current home and finances. In other words, rather negative reasons are steering people towards choosing the RCC as their new dwelling. By looking at the two intramural types through an SWB-lens, linking the actual living experiences to the architectural environment and the background of these concepts, we hope to retrieve more insights into how SWB can occur.

In the next chapter, we will make a transition from the objective characteristics towards the main topic of our research: subjective well-being, and more specifically SWB linked to the architectural environment.

THE BELGIAN INTRAMURAL CONCEPTS THROUGH AN SWB LENS

In this section, we study the two earlier mentioned Belgian intramural care concepts through an SWB lens in order to learn more on the question, if and how the built environment impacts on living experiences and SWB.

Methodology and procedure

For the SWB research, the authors have selected one case per architectural intramural care concept: one RCC (located in a small provincial town, with 62 residents) and one small-scale

living facility (a city center dwelling for 7 residents in a large city). The first author has immersed herself into these two care facilities by performing volunteer work and joining personnel and residents in spending one entire day at the concerned facility. During the volunteer work the first author has also informally spoken to residents about subjects concerning their living quality, level of entertainment, care provision etc., as well as to personnel regarding the amount of time they could spend per resident, level of work pressure, and activities done with residents, etc.

Based on the proper experiences and ethnographic research data of the first author, a SWB analysis was executed. We emphasize that this analysis is not a systematic, full-scale SWB comparison between the two facilities. It stands for the detection of important notable elements influencing SWB, intrinsic to the specific architectural care concept, and is detectable after spending a day at the elderly care facility, performing tasks of the personnel and talking to residents. Therefore, this research functions as a first exploration of the Belgian intramural residential care landscape regarding SWB.

Since our research scope is SWB linked to (interior) architecture, we only elaborate on the first author's experiences that can be brought back or linked to the (experience of the) architectural environment, or features linked to the architectural set-up of the intramural care concepts. Living experiences linked to other factors, for instance staff and care provision, will not be discussed since they do not have a direct link to the built environment.

Chosen SWB lens as analysis instrument

We opted for Desmet and Pohlmeier's Positive Design Framework (2013) as our SWB lens. This framework emphasizes stimulating positive design that contributes to a person's feeling of subjective well-being (Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013). It is developed from a product design background, and states that three ingredients; namely personal pleasure, meaning, and virtue will stimulate human flourishing when accomplished altogether in one design. The framework can be interpreted as a working instrument for a designer, on how to design a product in ways that people can experience the three ingredients in order for them to flourish. The fact that it is specifically developed with the purpose of increasing people's well-being, is an interesting approach that can also apply to architectural designers.

Therefore, this framework seems to be a relevant tool to study SWB in the field of architectural design. The user, in this case the residents of residential care concepts, and their living experiences in and reactions to the environment are placed first. This framework allows us to research if and where 'pleasure', 'personal significance', and 'sense of virtue' of the resident can occur with regards to the physical environment. All three ingredients are necessary in order for a person to flourish and thrive, which is an element that former studies have acknowledged to be important for elderly persons residing in residential care (e.g., Bergland & Krikevold, 2006). We believe this user-centered analysis of residential care architecture can provide us with valuable information on how the architectural

design of care concepts can enhance a positive feeling of well-being by generating pleasure, meaning, and sense of virtue to the resident. This approach is an interesting addition to existing research that in most cases reflects on how existing design outlooks in SWB literature are present in residential care architecture (see Lee, 2007; Stevens et. al, 2013).

Results

The RCC

We believe that the physical environment is an important parameter that relates to the element of 'pleasure' that is part of the Positive Design framework. Interviews with residents of the RCC for instance demonstrated that they specifically appreciate the fact that they are allowed to arrange and decorate their private (bed)room, i.e. that they have the freedom to furnish and decorate it. This spatial opportunity for the residents (i.e., the potential act of designing) seems to generate a certain effect, that is, residents have the possibility of taking control of their physical environment. When we apply the three ingredients framework on these activities, it is not difficult to believe that the act of designing the interior of the private room can evoke positive feelings. Not only can pleasure be found in the action of designing and decorating, but also in admiring the 'end product'. Another important result of this activity, is that the elderly person experiences a feeling of control over this particular space, which evokes feelings of pride and the awareness of an achievement, which is indicated to be important for the elderly (Percival, 2002). Also, this act of designing provides an opportunity for social interaction with other residents, since the possibility arises that the elderly person has performed the furnishing and decorating activity in such a great way that other residents drop by to have a look, admire it, and give compliments to the concerned resident. This so-called side effect of the act of designing (social interaction) can generate feelings of pleasure. On the other hand, the act of designing a room and therefore taking control of it also provides an opportunity for the resident to explore skills and even display them, which could be a key to experiencing a sense of virtue. Taking this even further, designing a room, training and displaying skills, and socially interacting in it with others, can spur the elderly person to altruistic behaviour in the form of helping fellow residents design their rooms. This altruistic behaviour could also trigger a sense of virtue.

In brief, the simple act of allowing residents to equip, set up, and decorate their proper (bed)room can be labeled as an act of positive design, since all three ingredients are met to allow the resident to flourish.

This privilege of personal decoration is not allowed in the communal spaces of the RCCs, spaces in which a lot of daytime is spent. The fact that the residents do not have an influence in the design of these spaces can — according to our view — be considered as a missed opportunity concerning SWB, although we are aware that practical arguments play a role in this respect too. However, we are convinced that there are possibilities to introduce minor design options and give the

control over these spaces (partially) to residents. Taking into account that residents in RCCs spend most of the daytime in these spaces, it could be an interesting intervention to open these up to certain forms of personal influences for residents.

Other links of SWB and the built environment of RCCs can be found in the strict day- and nighttime regime of RCCs. Interviews have shown that most residents experience unpleasant feelings when being obliged to rise earlier and consume their meals on other (and fixed) times than they were used to when living in their own private home. This generates the feeling of loss of control. Residents experience the feeling of being deprived of the freedom of living life at their own pace, and directing their day in a way they want to, which could pose a possible threat to the residents' self-esteem. However, the possibility exists that small changes in this rigid structure of RCCs can avoid this threat and even trigger positive feelings by residents. The installation of a buffet restaurant for instance, instead of standard meal services, can potentially lead to more freedom for the residents in terms of rising-time in the morning, the time they consume a meal, and the ability of making impulsive choices on what they want to eat, etc. These small changes all contribute to experiencing feelings of pleasure and personal meaning, which are two of the three ingredients needed for potential flourishing, according to the framework. When we search for virtuous behaviour as a result of this intervention, thoughts come to mind that residents can, for instance, incite themselves to choose more healthy dishes from the buffet options in order to contribute to a healthy living attitude. However, this virtuousness is less clear.

The small-scale living facility

The second intramural concept is the small-scale living facility. This architectural care concept offers a homelike environment to a small number of residents (<10), whereby the aim is to instill an actual single family home, in terms of spatial configuration, size, room, typology etc. This perception of 'homelikeness' has shown to be a very important factor for elderly persons in residential care (e.g. Brummett, 1997; Peace, 2005; Fay 2012). Also, this 'homelikeness', and moreover the architectural layout of a single family home, provides the opportunity for actions and experiences that apply to the three ingredients of Desmet and Pohlmeier's Positive Design Framework. In this intramural concept, residents are able to actively participate in the household chores. The facility is ran by nurses that function as a kind of 'housekeeper' and is dressed in regular clothes, which invigorates the 'homelike' character of the environment. The architectural layout of the house is similar to that of a single-family home, and the 'communal spaces' in this case consist of a living room with dining area and an attached open kitchen with a kitchen table. In contrast to most intramural care concepts in which meals are cooked in an industrial kitchen out of eyesight, in this care concept meals are home cooked in the kitchen area by the nurse and usually with the help of residents. This homelike concept has the side effect of providing the living area with smells of fresh coffee and cooking flavors, which is a sensory experience that can evoke

joyful feelings. The fact that the residents are in direct contact with the open kitchen when entering the living room, and can freely walk in whenever they want and have a snack, or even help in the cooking process, provides them with a sense of control over their daily activities, and gives them the ability to test their (cooking) skills and even display them, which contributes to their self-esteem. Observations have shown that the majority of the residents chose to actively participate in the cooking processes. They perform tasks sitting together and chatting, and are even taking initiatives in assisting each other when performing more difficult tasks like cutting small pieces of vegetables. This act of participation in preparing a meal, triggers social interaction that gives a sense of pleasure, but also evokes altruistic behaviour that can provide a sense of meaning and worthiness to the resident. The fact that residents are cooking a meal for their fellow residents can evoke feelings of pride and virtue since they are behaving in a good, altruistic way, and are contributing to the welfare of others. On the other hand, residents are never obliged to participate in activities, but rather are given the opportunity, which also contributes to their sense of 'freedom' and 'independence' in taking their own decisions and acting on them, which implies personal significance.

This small-scale care concept puts the emphasis on enhancing residents' pleasure and self-esteem, and the architectural layout of the facility is an important factor in the realization hereof. Another good example relates to the case's outdoor patio, which is partially arranged as a garden in the function of one of the current residents. This resident has the freedom of entering the patio whenever he feels the need to. In this way, in the intramural facility he can continue his old time habit of gardening. This activity provides him firstly with short-term pleasure, when actually working in the garden, secondly, with meaning and personal achievement when over-viewing the garden and its growing greens and being able to harvest vegetables, and thirdly with a sense of virtue, when he accomplishes a garden that is well-maintained, in order and that provides the residents with fresh vegetables. This interesting intervention of adapting the environment to personal wishes of residents, is a noble, SWB enhancing idea, but the remark must be made that it is relatively easier to make changes in a small scale facility with only a small number of residents, instead of in a larger scale RCC-facility with a larger number of residents that all carry their proper wishes.

Another interesting remark is that personal items are not banned from the kitchen area and living room in this small-scale setting. Interviews with the main nurse of the facility also revealed that the furniture and decoration items were not chosen purely based on their OWB-performance (e.g., user friendliness and safety), but they had to be a compromise between user friendliness and home likeness.

We can see that this small-scale living concept has potential for residents to be able to flourish in their physical environment, since the built environment in combination with the organization of the concept, responds well to the three ingredients of Desmet and Pohlmeier's Positive Design Framework.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In this paper, we discussed two intramural care concepts in Belgium on their objective characteristics and on how aspects related to their built environment affect residents' SWB by applying Desmet and Pohlmeier's Positive Design Framework of (2013) as a lens for looking at the built environment and how it is experienced.

Analyzing instances of intramural care in Belgium on the potential link between the architectural environment and SWB enhancing experiences, suggests that it is more difficult to accomplish the three ingredients of the Positive Design Framework in the specific care concept of the RCC than in the small-scale living concept. We must take into account that the organizational structure and the larger number of residents living together in a RCC complicate the process of trying to provoke SWB through initiatives relating to pleasure, meaning, and virtue. According to our preliminary analyses, the architectural concept of small-scale living seems to carry more potential of increasing residents' SWB. Not only the architectural layout of the physical environment as a single family home, but also the way in which the small-scale living concept is organized to fit the framework. The user-centered approach in which the resident is the key figure around which the personnel operates, and according to which the built environment is shaped to a certain degree, together with the architectural homelike atmosphere, has the ability to enhance SWB. This is an interesting starting point for further research.

Our research and the discussion of results concerned case studies, and the insights originated in an analysis of the first author's experiences in the concerned elderly housing concepts. The results could be furthered and strengthened by also discussing the set-up, organization, and experience of the concepts with the concerned stakeholders (architects, interior architects, paying clients and 'users' / inhabitants). Also, this research could be furthered by analyzing other types of elderly care facilities. For now, we have put the emphasis on the RCC and the small scale living facility, respectively a fixed value and an interesting 'newbie' in the Belgian residential care landscape. These two are the top two types in Belgian intramural care, since they are connected to our way of living and rooted in our cultural system. Looking at other types of elderly care facilities could also reveal cultural differences, which can be very interesting in SWB research linked to the built environment.

Also, in this research we focused on a number of (interior) architectural elements. We acknowledge that a lot more can be said concerning other elements in those built environments. We chose to highlight a few elements that immediately caught the attention of the first author and were estimated to have a major influence on SWB. By addressing only a few elements, we enabled ourselves to go into detail and also formulate our proper ideas as spatial experts to find solutions to these SWB-threatening elements or circumstances. However, for future research it could be interesting to try to list more environmental elements influencing SWB in a specific built environment.

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DESIGN FOR HEALTHY BEHAVIOR

DESIGN INTERVENTIONS AND STAGES OF CHANGE

Geke D.S. Ludden
University of Twente
✉ g.d.s.ludden@utwente.nl
Paul Hekkert
Delft University of Technology
✉ p.p.m.hekkert@tudelft.nl

ABSTRACT

Designers have increasingly used the capacity of design to influence human behavior and consequently to address the challenges that our society faces. One of these challenges is the rise of 'lifestyle diseases', such as obesity and diabetes. A change towards a more healthy lifestyle could in many cases prevent or diminish such diseases, which would reduce demands and costs in care. Moreover, it could lead to a higher level of wellbeing for many people.

In response to this challenge, designers and computer scientists have created interventions that help people adopt a healthier lifestyle. We argue that designers need to consider the different stages that people go through to durably change their behavior. In this paper, we discuss how design interventions aimed at adopting a healthier lifestyle correspond to different stages in the Transtheoretical Model of Health Behavior Change. Furthermore, we discuss how designers could design for stages of change.

KEYWORDS: *Design, health, lifestyle, behavior change, stages of change.*

INTRODUCTION

Design influences human behavior and designers are increasingly effective in using this capacity of design. Think, for example, of how the interactive crystals created by Dutch designer Daan Roosegaarde persuade, or rather, invite people to play and interact with them, and, consequently, with one another. Or, think of how a simple product such as a bowl, designed by Jan Hoekstra for Royal VKB, could persuade people to eat the right portion of food. This bowl tilts when filled with a certain weight, telling its user that the correct portion size was reached.

By using the power of design to influence people's behavior, designers can and are making successful contributions to diminishing some of the large societal problems that we face. One of these problems is the increase in so-called 'lifestyle diseases' such as obesity and diabetes (Lee et al., 2012) that negatively affect our well-being and lead to increasing costs and demands in healthcare. A large proportion of modern society does not live up to the recommended guidelines for healthy behavior. Lifestyle changes could counter this.

In the development of interventions aimed at changing lifestyle behavior, next to psychologists, researchers from two other fields are active; designers and computer scientists, creating, for example, interactive systems that try to persuade people to lead a more active life. The set types of non-personal interventions are promising because they could potentially reach a larger group of people than traditional interventions can (Norman et al., 2007). Furthermore, people using these interventions could potentially use them at any place and at any point in time (Fogg, 2010).

However, in the design of current non-person interventions, the motivational state of the user of the intervention is often not considered. In health psychology, stages of change models are used to define the different stages people go through from the moment they start thinking about changing their behavior to the moment that they have durably changed it. The stages differ with respect to how ready and willing people are to change, i.e. their motivational state. A dominant model is the transtheoretical model of behavior change (TTM), by Prochaska and di Clemente (1992). Designing an intervention in such a way that it matches the typical behavior of a person at

a certain stage seems logical and it is, in fact, what many psychologists do when they develop traditional health interventions (e.g., Johnson et al., 2008). However, considering the stage of change that a person is in is generally not part of a designer's approach.

In this paper, we will present and discuss design interventions and how they correspond to the different stages of change in the TTM. Finally, we will provide recommendations on how to better target design interventions to the motivational state of users of these interventions.

STAGES OF CHANGE; THE TTM

In their work on health behavior change, Prochaska et al. (1992, 1997) identified ten distinct processes of change from a comparative theoretical study. When they presented these processes to their research participants, they reported that they used different processes of change at different times, thus revealing that behavior change follows a series of stages. Prochaska et al. (1992), suggest that to make a durable health change, whether it is to quit smoking, to eat a more healthy diet (e.g., less fat), or to increase physical activity, people pass through five stages: precontemplation, contemplation, preparation, action, and maintenance. In the first three stages, people build motivation to change, and in the last two stages people act. In this process, people may move through stages more or less quickly. For example, some people are stuck in the contemplation stage for long periods of time (chronic contemplation). Also, many people relapse from action or maintenance stages to an earlier stage, mostly to contemplate or prepare for another serious attempt at action. Finally, a durable behavior change can be reached. Figure 1 shows the stages with the descriptions of the motivational state of people in these stages (from Prochaska & Velicer, 1997).

Next to the five stages of change, Prochaska et al. (1992) describe ten processes of change that people who (self-)changed their behavior reported to have used to progress through the stages. These processes are also depicted in Figure 1, below the stages of change in which people reported to have used them most. It has been argued that these processes of change should guide the development of intervention programs, because people need to be able to use these processes to

progress through the stages (Prochaska & Velicer, 1997). Similarly, we would like to argue that non-person (or design-) interventions should support or enable people to use the different processes of change in different stages.

Psychologists have used the TTM to design their interventions so that they match the motivational state that people are in (e.g., Johnson et al., 2008). Research in the field with these 'traditional' interventions has shown dramatic improvements in retention and progress using stage-matched interventions (Prochaska & Velicer, 1997). Especially retention (adherence) is an aspect that has been found to be problematic for non-person interventions. Kelders et al. (2012) found that adherence to, for example, web-based interventions was very low. Often, these type of interventions are very action-oriented and do not necessarily comply with the motivational states of users. In the following, we will discuss how design interventions can address the correct stage of change by presenting for each stage of change two examples of matching design interventions. For each intervention, we discuss how it supports the processes of change that people have reported to use in that stage. In our examples, we use design interventions aiming at eating a healthier diet or at increasing physical activity. These two behavioral goals are often used for non-person interventions, the latter especially in computer science because they can easily rely on sensors in mobile phones that can be used to track people's physical behavior.

Motivation building; (pre)contemplation

In the first two stages of the TTM, the precontemplation and contemplation stage, people built motivation to change. In these stages, people are not aware of a need to change; they are not yet ready to change. People are contemplating whether changing has more benefits than drawbacks for them, they are moving their 'decisional balance' (Prochaska & Velicer, 1997, p. 40). In these stages, a design intervention should probably have the form of a general (publicly available), rather than a personal intervention, because people will not yet be motivated to buy or even to start using a personal intervention. Interventions in these stages should have an emphasis on raising awareness of the importance of and the benefits of changing. In the case of interventions aimed at persuading people to change their lifestyle, the importance and the benefits of a healthy lifestyle must be stretched.

Figure 1. The five stages of change of the TTM and the ten processes of change.

Precontemplation stage

The precontemplation stage is the stage in which people are not intending to take action within the next six months. People in this stage are avoiding to read, think, or talk about their unhealthy behavior.

1. *Design intervention for eating a healthier diet:* in their work on using strategies from behavioral economics to persuade people to make healthy choices, Lee et al. designed several interventions to promote healthy snacking in the workplace (Lee et al., 2011). These interventions aimed to present choices in a way that leverages people's decision processes and induces them to make self-beneficial choices. For example, one of the interventions they designed was a robot that would present two types of snacks, whereby it was made easier to pick a healthy snack (apple) than it was to pick a less healthy snack (cookie).

Change Process addressed: The example described above could be seen as a form of *stimulus control*: it removes a cue for an unhealthy habit (eating cookies is made slightly more difficult), and adds a prompt for a healthier alternative (picking the apple as a snack is made slightly easier) (Prochaska & Velicer, 1997). N.B., from Figure 1 it can be seen that stimulus control was mentioned as a process of change that people report to use in later stages (action or maintenance stages). We will come back to this in our discussion.

2. *Design intervention for increasing physical activity:* A few years ago, The Dutch Voedingscentrum (Centre for Food) released the game 'Na-aapje' (which could be translated as 'little copy-cat' but literally would be translated as 'little copy-monkey'). Na-aapje is a children's game that is designed to raise awareness with children that fruit and vegetables are healthy diet choices. The monkey in the game has to collect fruits and vegetables and the child scores high by collecting as many fruits and vegetables as possible.

Change Process addressed: *Consciousness raising.* Consciousness raising is aimed at increasing awareness of causes and consequences of problem behaviors (Prochaska & Velicer, 1997). In the example of Na-aapje, awareness of what healthy choices are is raised.

Contemplation stage

In order to move through the contemplation stage, people have to gradually become more conscious of their unhealthy behavior. Eventually, their 'decisional balance' has to shift; people have to start to see changing their lifestyle as more beneficial and/or desirable for them than not changing their lifestyle.

1. *Design intervention for eating a healthier diet:* Brown et al. (2006) developed a system for college students to raise awareness of how (un)healthy their lifestyle was and how they could make changes towards a healthier lifestyle. To do so, they used a technique using photographs of food and activities developed by Frost and Smith (2003), and designed a mobile phone application to implement this

technique. The result was FotoFit..FotoFit visualizes activity and diet habits and helps users reflect on their lifestyle.

Change Process addressed: The FotoFit system uses the process of *Self-reevaluation*; the assessment of one's self-image with (and without) a particular unhealthy habit (Prochaska & Velicer, 1997). The FotoFit system enables people to more objectively review themselves and their diet and exercise habits, and thereby raises awareness of their unhealthy habits.

2. *Design intervention for increasing physical activity:* 'Bouncers' is a wallpaper on smart phones of a group of friends that visualises everyone's activity through moving circles. In this abstract way it tells its users about their movement in relation to that of their friends (Nelson, 2012).

Change Process addressed: 'Bouncers' also uses a form of self-reevaluation; the circles represent someone's activity relative to that of others and thereby allows for comparison and evaluation of one's behavior.

Getting ready and acting; preparation, action and maintenance

Preparation stage

This stage is characterized by getting ready to change once the user has decided that some change in behavior is desirable.

1. *Design intervention for eating a healthier diet:* Imagine a canteen in which salad ladles in different colors help people to make healthier diet choices. A display explaining the color code of the ladles informs people in this canteen about the type of salad ingredients that you can eat a lot of (green), the type that you can eat a small amount of (yellow), and the ones you should scoop most moderately in your salad (red) in order to eat a healthy salad.

Change Process addressed: social liberation; Social liberation involves creating opportunities for people to change their behavior. Prochaska and Velicer (1997) name smoke-free zones and salad bars as examples. This salad bar not only offers people the opportunity to eat salad in a canteen, the ladles also make it easier to assemble a healthy salad.

2. *Design intervention for increasing physical activity:* in the Netherlands, health insurance company Menzis offers its clients the possibility to collect points for healthy behavior (e.g., not smoking will give you a certain amount of points). Clients can use these points to buy healthy products and services. For example, a route application for mobile phones was offered (AbelLife, 2014) that makes it easy to find nice and inspiring walking and cycling routes.

Change Process addressed: *Self-liberation*, also called willpower, is gaining the belief that you are able to change and the commitment to act on that belief (Prochaska & Velicer 1997). Knowing how to act in order to change (and preferably having multiple action choices) is very important in this situation. By offering walking routes (among other options to increase physical activity) to its clients Menzis supports this process.

Action stage

In the action stage, people have successfully changed their behavior for a short period of time (generally less than six months is used as a criterion). People in this stage can benefit from interventions that help them to avoid problematic behavior and that help them discover new healthy behaviors.

1. *Design intervention for eating a healthier diet:* In Amsterdam, a new concept of a food store was recently introduced that helps people avoid choosing less healthy (but quick) alternatives in the supermarket. This store, 'Bilder & de Clercq', aims to facilitate people to easily cook a healthy and tasty evening meal. The store is set up by recipe, and visitors can directly find the (fresh) ingredients needed at the recipe of their choice.

Change Process addressed: In their new concept for a food store, Bilder & de Clercq make use of the process of *counterconditioning*; healthier options for evening meals are more accessible to people, in the process, people learn healthier behaviors and can substitute this for problem behaviors (such as choosing the unhealthy but fast options for evening meals).

2. *Design intervention for increasing physical activity:* Philips Directlife activity monitor, this is a personal device that people own and use for a longer period of time to keep track of their behavior. The Directlife system consists of a personal activity monitor and personalized coaching tips based on the data that the activity monitor feeds into the system. For example, the personal coach will suggest going for walks during lunchtime if the measured activity is below a set goal.

Change Processes addressed: Helping relationships and counterconditioning. For *counterconditioning* to take place, people need to learn healthier behaviors that can substitute for problem behaviors. For example, in the Directlife coach, someone may be suggested to bike to work instead of driving to be more physically active. The process *helping relationships* is also part of this system; the coaching tips that are given are not fully personalized but they are designed to simulate a personal coach who is supportive of the behavioral change.

Maintenance stage

People in the maintenance stage have been successful in changing their behavior for a longer period of time (over six months). They are working to prevent relapse and need to be motivated to keep up the newly achieved behavior.

1. *Design intervention for a healthier diet:* The Sense Mother system is a good example of a system that is designed to support people after they have decided to change their behavior in a certain way and need motivation to continue. The system exists of a 'Mother' and several 'motion cookies' that can be attached to almost anything. In this way, the cookies can help people track their activity, whilst also informing them whether they drank enough water. Multiple other applications are possible, all to be set by the user of the system. Reports are given through a storyboard on cell phone or tablet.

Change Process addressed: Contingency management: this process includes reinforcements of 'good' behavior, the storyboard reports that the Sense Mother system is an example, but the system also facilitates setting up competitions between users, thus enforcing group recognition and stimulation.

2. *Design intervention for increased physical activity:* The bowl designed by Jan Hoekstra for Royal VKB can be seen as a design intervention matching this stage. Although (as most interventions presented here) it wasn't originally designed to serve as an intervention that can help people to keep on eating the right portion of food, it may well be used as such.

Change Process addressed: Stimulus control: several studies have shown that small structural changes in personal environments can help reduce the unknowing overconsumption of food: e.g., eating from a smaller plate and food in smaller packages influence how much people eat (Wansink, 2004).

TOWARDS A FRAMEWORK TO DESIGN FOR HEALTHY BEHAVIOR

The examples of interventions that match a certain stage of change presented previously show that for each stage, different characteristics of interventions are important. The interventions presented here were not specifically designed to match a certain stage but in theory, they would work better for certain stages than for others. It could even be counterproductive to offer people a certain intervention that does not match the stage of change that they are in (Prochaska & Velicer, 1997).

However, to further increase the effectiveness of design interventions (non-person interventions), designers could benefit from adopting stages of change theory. In recent years, designers have become used to following a user-centred approach. Adopting stages of change in their design process would enable them to design for the way people actually behave, and not for the way they want them to behave (Norman, 2007). This may seem contradictory, since the aim of these interventions is to change people (or at least their behavior). However, as Prochaska and Velicer (1997) put it: instead of expecting people to match the needs of the interventions, the interventions need to match the motivational states of people. Only if interventions are recognised as matching their motivational states, people will adopt them and use them, which is essential for moving through the stages of change.

The processes of change can serve as a starting point for the design of stage-matched interventions. However, the distribution of processes over the stages may well be somewhat different from a design point of view. The original distribution was made based on the strategies people mentioned they had used to support their behavior change. A design intervention may, on the one hand, aim to support the use of these processes of change in a certain stage. On the other hand, a design intervention could also aim to elicit a process of change

more unobtrusively. For example, Prochaska and Velicer (1997) place the process of change *stimulus control* under the stages of change of action and maintenance. Apparently, people use these processes in these stages. Our example of an intervention in the precontemplation stage shows that the same process could also be used by a designer to seduce, or to nudge (Thaler & Sunstein, 2008) those people still in the earlier stages of change to make further healthier choices. It should be noted, however, that in this case, although the intervention may have a positive effect on healthy choices at the moment a person encounters this intervention, the intervention does not directly help a person in moving on to the next stage. For this to happen, people should be made aware of their choices.

On another note, the same design intervention could mean different things (and therefore work differently) for people in different stages. For example, as we described, for someone in the preparation stage, the colored ladles in a salad bar could work as an enabling element, helping to make the right choices, whereas it would raise awareness of the mere existence of healthier choices for people in earlier stages.

Based on our analysis of design interventions with the examples presented, we propose a preliminary framework for stage-matched design interventions (Figure 2). In this framework, processes of change, stages of change, design strategies, and their relationships are represented. The processes of change are not strictly connected to each of the stages, because, as we have seen from the examples above, designers may use different processes to design interventions for different stages. Four types of design strategies have been defined that lead to four different (design) aims: ‘raising awareness’, ‘enabling’, ‘motivating’, and ‘fading out’. As can be seen from Figure 2, the design strategies spread over multiple stages.

Design strategies for ‘raising awareness’ can move people into a process of behavior change, these are the strategies that help people evaluate the choices they have made so far and place them in a new perspective. The result should be that they move into the preparation stage because they are ready (i.e., willing, feel capable) to change. Next, design strategies that are aimed at ‘enabling’ are in order. We use the term

enabling to characterize interventions that support people in making the right choices; choices that lead to adoption of a healthier lifestyle and that fit their personal situation and preferences. In other words, interventions should incorporate strategies that empower people to create their own action plan. Well into the action and maintenance stages, *motivating* becomes the primary aim of interventions. In these stages, people have already changed and strategies that can support them to maintain changes or to help find new possibilities for change are needed. Finally, in entering the termination stage, right before a durable behavior change is reached, design interventions should incorporate a *fading out* phase. Prochaska and Velicer (1997) found in their clinical trials a negative effect of stopping personal counselling, people had become dependent on the social support and social monitoring and performed worse after these influences were withdrawn. A similar effect could be expected for personal design interventions.

While this framework begins to explain the relationships between health behavior change and design interventions, it also raises questions. First, we have proposed four types of design strategies that should help people progress through the different stages. Each type, however, may come in several variations. In current design interventions, for example, many different strategies to motivate have been explored. More research (and design) is needed to further explore the various possible strategies and the effectiveness of each. Secondly, we have emphasized that design interventions should help people to move through the different stages. This raises the issue of what happens in the interaction with an intervention when someone moves through various stages. As a consequence, the intervention a person uses may at some point not be as effective because it was designed for a stage that the person has moved beyond. Perhaps, at some point, a person should adopt a different type of intervention addressing a new aim. Or, alternatively, an intervention should adapt (or be adapted) to the stages. How (and if) such a dynamic intervention would work has not yet been explored. Finally, within the various stages and strategies, the issue of adherence needs further exploration. Again, within action and maintenance stages adherence has gained some attention, but in earlier stages adherence has hardly been addressed.

Figure 2. Preliminary framework for stage-matched design interventions.

CONCLUSION & DISCUSSION

In this paper, we have presented a variety of existing non-person interventions, ranging from web-based interventions, to mobile phone applications, to separate interactive products (or product-service systems) and simple physical products. Although the examples presented here give insight into how design interventions could support a user's progression through the different stages of change, a larger review of existing interventions is needed to support our claim that most of the current interventions are action oriented, and to further explore how existing interventions would match the stages of change. To our knowledge, a complete review of non-person interventions that includes non-interactive designs has not yet been made.

In their review of eHealth interventions for physical activity and dietary behavior change, Norman et al. (2007) discuss three generations of eHealth interventions. The first generation facilitated tailoring of interventions using computers (e.g., tailored feedback messages), interventions of the second generation allowed for direct interaction between users and technology, and the third (now emerging) generation of eHealth interventions makes use of new platforms (mobile devices) with new functions (sensing, location-based knowledge presentation, etc.). A similar view on the future of persuasive technologies is also held by Chatterjee and Price (2009). The examples discussed here have shown second and third generation interventions. In spite of the variety of interventions presented here and referred to in these review studies and outlooks, we would like to argue that the possible solutions for the design of (e)health interventions could have an even broader range. Within each stage, more creative and challenging solutions could surely be found when designers consider the motivational states of people in these stages, and the processes of change that could be used. To name a few: in the maintenance stage, the change process 'contingency management' could be supported by offering people a device in the form of a closed box in which they can place a personal reward that they will obtain when certain (measurable) goals are met for a period of time. The box will only open when the goals are met. With such a device, the (digital and surreal) rewarding system, which many web-based or mobile applications use, could be replaced by a real-life award. In the earlier stages, alternative and more interactive awareness raising interventions could be imagined. For example, one could think of a public screen in a waiting area at a station that senses activity of the people in that area and displays tips to increase activity. This screen could even be coupled to activity enabling devices that people could use while waiting. The possibilities are endless and can be found beyond interactive devices with sensors that people carry around.

Most of the examples discussed here are conceptual designs or prototypes and only a few of them are completely worked out applications that are commercially available. As a consequence, the practical implications of these and other concepts, and how effective they would be, are largely unknown.

This calls for more in the field controlled trials with design interventions. Field trials are also needed to determine which design strategies can be best used at which stage of change. Also, the possible positive effects of dynamic interventions (that adapt when the user moves through the stages) need to be further investigated. Therefore, (the first author of this paper) aims to design interventions which will be subject to a field experiment with a between subjects design, with people in three different stages of action in order to test whether they are indeed more effective (in terms of increase in activity, acceptance, and adherence) for the relevant stage. Next to this, a dynamic intervention will be created and compared to a static intervention in a randomised controlled trial (RCT).

Eventually, adopting stages of change theory to design for behavior change aimed at adopting a healthier lifestyle will help designers to design interventions in such a way that they will be more easily accepted by people, increasing the use of these products and services. This will have a positive impact on people's well being and society at large: Successful adoption of interventions aimed at healthy living by more people will eventually lead to a healthier population which will lower demands and costs in care.

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ASSISTIVE TECHNOLOGY, DESIGN AND GAMBARRA:

PERCEPTUAL NOTIONS OF DIFFERENT PENCIL THICKENERS THROUGH THE DS PROTOCOL

Juliana Maria Moreira Soares
Universidade Federal de São Carlos
✉ julianammsoares@gmail.com
Cleyton Fernandes Ferrarini
Universidade Federal de São Carlos
✉ cleyton@ufscar.br
Andrea Regina Martins Fontes
Universidade Federal de São Carlos
✉ andrea@dep.ufscar.br
Miguel Ángel Aires Borrás
Universidade Federal de São Carlos
✉ maborras@ufscar.br
Larissa Corrêa Manoel
Universidade Federal de São Carlos
✉ larissacm.to@uol.com.br

ABSTRACT

This study intends to evaluate five models of a product of the assistive technology area, known as pencil grip, used for ergonomic adequacy, through an evaluation protocol called the Semantic Differential (SD). This object is widely used in rehabilitation environments, involving learning and recreational activities, as it is the case of the institution chosen for this research, located in Sorocaba (SP — Brazil). Through DS protocol, it was sought to analyze the users' perception of the products with respect to subjective aspects. It was also in the issues of this research, the discussion of the use of homemade adapted models within the assistive technology, called *gambiarra* in Brazil (kludge or workaround, or even a Do It Yourself product), since four of the five models tested were made this way.

KEYWORDS: *assistive technology; design; semantic differential; adaptation; disability.*

INTRODUCTION

About 15% of the world's population has some sort of disability, representing a total estimate of one billion people, according to an United Nations research.¹ The majority of this population lives in developing countries, where a considerable portion does not attend any school or paid activity. Assistive technology, more than the technical concept of physical contribution needed for the disabled, has connected its significance to the function of the social, environmental, and economic inclusion of the individual, emphasizing the need to search for changes in societies. The concept of assistive

technology can be summarized as the creation and use of devices that supplement, enhance, maintain, or give back the residual capacities of persons with disabilities, and aims at maximizing the functional performance of the individual, thus, decreasing their impossibilities (Hogetop & Santarosa, 2002). Galvão Filho and Damasceno (2008, p.4) still propose another definition, also with emphasis on the question of self-sufficiency of the individual, as follows: 'Every tool, resource or process used in order to provide greater independence and autonomy a disabled person'.²

1. Information reported on the UN website, available from: <http://www.un.org/disabilities/default.asp?id=18>. [26th November, 2013].

2. Translated by the author. Original text: 'Tecnología asistida es toda herramienta, recurso o proceso utilizado con el fin de proporcionar una mayor independencia y autonomía a la persona con discapacidad'.

The market supply reality in assistive technology is quite complex in developing countries, like Brazil, where the variety of this kind of product is scarce, and the costs are considerably high in many cases. Despite the growing development in the industrial and scientific areas, many components or even complete products are imported, increasing the final cost to the consumer. This scenario points out many needs, and among them, the need for the development of homemade products, through so-called *gambiarra*, a Brazilian word for kludge, which are specific utility improvisations involving determined contexts, such as socioeconomic factors, the use in which the industrial product is inserted, and the deconstruction of the design process to which it is related (Bonfleur, 2013). Within this context of making and/or owning adaptations, there is also the possibility to customize the product, given that most subjective and specific user requirements about artifacts are hardly attended by the industrial product, since the pleasure of using certain objects can be based on different aspects, such as functionality, innovativeness, aesthetics, personal meaning, and social values, among others (Gotszsch, 2013; Tractinsky et al., 2000).

Seeking a correlation between the situations explained above, the present study sought to analyze, through the subjective usability evaluation of products called Semantic Differential (SD), five different models of an assistive technology product known as pencil grip, used by people with impaired handgrip, that requires a special ergonomic adequacy. Four of the five models used in the study were prepared in a homely way, and only one in this group was a manufactured product. The application of the DS model was carried out with the participation of professionals and patients of the chosen institution, located in Sorocaba (SP — Brazil), which offers rehabilitation activities for children and adolescents with multiple disabilities.

THE IMPORTANCE OF THIS INTERESTING OBJECT, THE PENCIL GRIP

The pencil grips are a type of assistive technology made for individuals who face some sort of restriction on the handgrip and adversities in motor coordination, which cause difficulties or impossibilities for holding objects with reduced dimensions. Individuals with Down Syndrome, some elderly people, and patients with certain types of cerebral palsy are cases that can experience this kind of difficulty, due to situations of muscle hypotonia and low motor coordination (Silva et al., 2009; Rantanen, 1999; Cruz, 2005). The pencil grip for ergonomic aid is an object made with a material of high to medium flexibility, usually in a tubular or triangular design, and with variable width (depends on the user), which fits the pencil that will be used in its interior.

It is noteworthy that the use of this type of object is not restricted only to pencils: it can be used in other artifacts that have the same or similar diameter to the hole (approximately sixty millimeters), and certain pen models, brushes, chalk waxes, and even cutlery for meals; thus being widely used in

other activities. In rehabilitation, learning, and recreational environments, such as the institution of the present study, the use of such materials has essential function to perform the tasks. One of the main activities carried out with the support of the grip in Creche Maria Claro is the artistic practices. Art and fantasy are important parts of the social and subjective training of the human being (Vygostky, 1986), carrying out activities in this field and encouraging the ludic and fanciful side is extremely important for the development of children and adolescents.

In addition, when talking about models of pencil grips available in the Brazilian market of assistive technology, according to a survey conducted by the author, it was found that this type of product has a high cost. Six models of this product were found, with prices ranging from 15 to 49 Brazilian *reais*. Such costs are significantly high, considering the Brazilian social reality of most of the disabled population, which is located in the lower socioeconomic strata. This cost also justifies the low amount of products present in these types of institutions that carry out activities persons with disabilities, despite its high need. Also, it is remarkable that the cost of assistive technologies can be a restrictive factor not only in developing countries (Kolatch, 2001; Kintsch et al., 2002; Parette, 2000; Pal et al., 2011; Inge & Targett, 2005).

THE ISSUE OF KLUDGE IN A.T.

Even with the existence of federal policies to grant certain models of assistive technology in Brazil (Brasil, 1999), as well as specific lines of public and private funding (Brasil, 2004), many products of the area are not covered by such processes. The existence of these projects demonstrates the high cost related to the possession of in this assistive technology, directly related to the fact that many components of the products being commercialized are originated outside Brazil, embedding in their values the expensive costs of these proceedings of importing — and in many cases the complete artifact is imported, due to the inexistence of a national industry that works in that particular niche. Numerous initiatives that support research and practice in the area of assistive technology are currently in emergence, but they do not yet supply these latent needs, especially of lower income populations and non-governmental institutions.

Through this situation, it becomes important to discuss the artisanal adaptation of regular products in order to fulfill the specific needs of users with disabilities. This *gambiarra* (kludge or workaround) then, taken by user, by family members, or caregivers, or even by other professionals in frequent contact, such as occupational and physical therapists, usually consists of the use of abundant or available resources, with the intention to play this role of substitution in relation with the existing material human needs (Bonfleur, 2013). Such modification, generating a *Do It Yourself* (DIY) artifact, interferes promptly in the most important industrial product dimensions: form, meaning, purpose, and its material composition — then, re-designing the product (Bonfleur, 2013).

All this communicative process, accomplished through the design of the products included in the operation of adaptation, is then intermediated and resignified by the user of such products that has become an assistive to technology. According to Bonfleur (2013), the subversion of design in *gambiarra* carries implications for multiple aspects of the product and may modify it in shape, purpose, or both. Thus, this improvised product acquires new conditions to meet important aspects to the user of these technologies, such as ergonomic aspects, providing a better adjustment to the disability in question, since the skills and impairments of all people (not only the disabled) make them unique (Kintsch et al., 2002); for example, emotional, providing greater customization, with the possibility to change aspects of their original design; and of course, the economic, since the adaptation, in general, is more financially viable than buying a new artifact.

In this way, the study sought to conduct a test of assistive technology products that were manually assembled, and also of the industrialized model. Trying to show the viability of this kind of practice, with emphasis on the issue of work based on the subjective and product customization, this approach was performed through the evaluation protocol called the DS, which will be explained in the next topic.

THE MODEL OF THE SEMANTIC DIFFERENTIAL (SD)

The technique of the Semantic Differential (SD) was introduced by Osgood, Taci, and Tanenbaum in 1957, and aims at exploring the emotional, subjective, or connotative meaning of concepts used by the study object, tangent to the attitude of the users, exposing the participants to a survey composed of several bipolar descriptors, separated from each other by a seven scale table (Likert scale), demanding the users to fill it in according to their perceptions (Brandalise, 2006; Andrade, 2007; Darnell, 2006; Solórzano, 2008). The approach of the SD has its onset in studies in psychology, being grounded in behaviorist models (related to processes of encoding and decoding of the individual), space models (which makes the assumption that a concept is connected to a given space), and metric models (linked to the formation of scales for the representation and technical operational dimension of mediation between the above concept and meaning) (Andrade, 2007).

The DS is a simple, quick, and easy comprehension test, which admits variations in its application (Lanutti et al., 2013), since it allows changes on the pairs of propositions according to which most suits the case study. Due to this flexibility, the DS is used in several areas beyond the field of psychology, like, for example, in studies within the sphere of architecture (Rudy, 2005), education (Evans, 1970; Whitney & Soukup, 1988), marketing (Markechová et al., 2013), and medicine (Lopes et al., 2011). Within the scope of the present research, other researches focusing on different products are found, such as juicers (Lanutti et al., 2013), analogue desk clocks (Sevener, 2003), calculators (Solórzano, 2008), and chairs (Lin et al., 2013).

Although no specific studies on the application of DS in the area of assistive technology have been found, this technique appears to be pertinent to this type of research, due to the fact that it focuses on the subjective aspect of the design choices. Many authors call attention to the welfare, which can have a great increase when there is a concern with the appearance of these products, along with its functionality (Kintsch & Depaula, 2002; Parette & Scherer, 2004; Pullin, 2009; Norman, 2004; Desmet, 2003; Hocking, 1999), taking into account the many variables that influence this process that inhibits the stigmatization of disabled citizen, such as socio-cultural issues present in the user surroundings (Parette & Scherer, 2004). Graham Pullin (2009) also draws attention the need a change in the medicalized perspective about the products in this area, towards the adoption of a social model and with more freedom, where interventions and experimentations are enabled through design, and attending more personal perspectives (mainly subjective and emotional ones).

METHODOLOGY

This study took place within the institution located in Sorocaba (SP — Brazil). A total of eight participants joined the study: two occupational therapist professionals, and six children with an average age of 10,16 years (standard deviation: 2,67 years), with different types of grips/ pencil grips. A total of eight children that used the apparatus were detected on the institution, but only six of them were able to join the research. It sought to follow a qualitative axis of data collection, looking for the construction of an analytical framework about the products tested, emphasizing the subjective aspect of the user identification with these artifacts.

For the perceptual evaluation, five models of pencil thickener were selected. Of the five models shown, four of them were made by adaptations, inspired by the literature of the area (Bersch, 2008; Galvão Filho, 2009), and based on some models in the market. The most popular model of the industrial product in the market was the fifth model chosen. All four models were handmade by the authors, each having an average cost close to one Brazilian real, and the institution owned the fifth model used. It is noted that there was familiarity by the participants with only one of the models exposed (the industrialized model).

The models of pencil grips are the following:

Figure 01. Model A, consisting of two distinct colors of EVA (green and lilac), with dimensions of 31mm by 13mm. Built by the technique of winding EVA with adhesive tape and styrofoam glue. Source: Authors.

Figure 02. Model B, consisting of two corks, with dimensions of 35mm by 10mm, in beige color. Constructed through the use of drill machine, with drill bit of 0.03 cm and 0.07 cm. Source: Authors.

Figure 03. Model C, made of two different colors of EVA (green and orange) and styrofoam, with dimensions of approx. 40mm by 123mm. Built by styrofoam with triangular cut and centrally holed, shrouded by EVA on the bases and sides, with adhesive tape and styrofoam glue. Source: Authors.

Figure 04. Model D, consisting of hard rubber with a diameter of 55mm. Source: Authors.

Figure 05. Model E, industrialized, consisting of expanded polyethylene black, with a diameter of 25mm by 105mm long. Source: Authors.

The characteristics of each model tested were verbally explained and specified to the participants. Those specifications were also distributed on a sheet. In an individual way, the objectives of the study were explained to the members of the research, and then the Term of Free Consent and Informed (called TCLE in Brazil) was distributed to be read and understood before the signing. All of the underage participants (under eighteen years) had the documents sent to their parents or legal guardians.

It was requested that the participants (children) color drawings on A4 sheets, making use of pencil grips, using each type at a distinct time, for approximately forty minutes. The children performed the test individually, doing it one at a time, with variable intervals between them (about ten to fifty minutes). During this period, the therapists' participants remained beside the child who was testing the artefacts, questioning them about the use of the products, capturing the verbalizations, and watching them intently, with the intention of jointly filling out the questionnaire. After the test and

completion of the questionnaire, another child initiated the activity. The test occurred inside one of the rooms of the institution, with the aid of an adjustable table with height and angle adjustments.

The assessment protocol of perception used was the DS, containing twelve pairs of bipolar adjectives and descriptive situations, permeated by seven scales (ranging from -3 to 3), to be filled according to the perception of the users. The descriptions used were about the possibilities in the use of the product, permeating the functional and subjective perception of the product features. They are not presented by affinity groups in the questionnaires. It is noted that the procedure of filling the DS forms occurred jointly, by the professional helper in activities with the patient, who was properly using the object. Audio recordings with the intention of recording the utterances and spontaneous statements were also used. Direct observation of the use of the artefact, after the end of the test was also made with the intention of analyzing the more natural user interaction with the objects in question (Yin, 2003).

STAGES OF THE RESEARCH	PROCEDURES
01. Theoretical review	Review of the issues that underlie the subject of this study (TA, studies about the DS protocol, issues of improvisations and aesthetic and emotional aspects of a product)
02. Search for models on the market and homemade models	Search on the internet and in bibliographies
03. Construction of the homemade models	Acquisition and collection of materials needed for the construction of such models
04. Selection of participants	Interview and open dialogues with professionals from the institution, looking for patients who use the product
05. Product testing and implementation of the questionnaire	Presentation of the TCLE (appendix A), presentation and use of the models, by the participants, besides the filling out of the questionnaire (appendix B)
06. Analysis of results	Analysis of the data collected with the support of the previously presented theoretical review
07. Development of hypotheses	From the analysis, hypotheses were elaborated to be further investigated in conjunction with the theories studied

Table 01. Table containing the summary of the methodology used in this research.

Source: Authors.

A total of twelve hours were necessary for the conduction of this research *in loco*, with the use of a digital recorder, generating three hours recording time, and a digital camera, resulting in the photographic material of 94 JPEG files .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Five scatter plots were generated with the average of the scores given by users, each one corresponding to one type of pencil grip. In the graphs, the adjectives are grouped by

affinity, in three semantic values, as defined by Medeiros and Ashton (2006, apud Lanutti et al., 2013); ludic (attractive/repulsive; serious/fun; beautiful/ugly; common/different); practical (light/heavy; stable/unstable; comfortable/uncomfortable; sturdy/fragile); and critical (secure/insecure; easy to use/difficult to use; effective/ineffective; anatomical/anti-anatomic). The group described by the authors above as an ideological group was excluded from the evaluation charts, because of the complexity of the adjectives in accordance with this theme, since the children are the audience of this study. The charts with the results can be visualized below:

Figure 06. Graph generated from the average of the responses of the model A. Source: Authors.

Figure 07. Graph generated from the average of the responses of the model B. Source: Authors.

Figure 08. Graph generated from the average of the responses of the model C. Source: Authors.

Figure 09. Graph generated from the average of the responses of the model D. Source: Authors.

Figure 10. Graph generated from the average of the responses of the model E. Source: Authors.

Between the assignments of various topics, a large standard deviation was noted, found in all models. This situation points to an important result in the development of products in the area of assistive technology, related to the deficiencies variability. It was noticed that some models, as for example the triangular orange one, functioned in a very effective way to assist the writing of half of the participants, but was shown to be an inconvenient product to others — the members of the research, even though having the same diagnosis (cerebral palsy), have different ways of gripping, which may not fit properly to that model, as the example of refined gripping, in the form of a clamp (Paiva, 2007), practiced by a participant. Also, this indicates a possibility of including a new pair of evaluations inside the DS model in cases of A.T. products, like 'it is very specific for the disability', or 'it's not specific for the disability'. This pair could be put inside the critical affinity group, for cases when the researcher is dealing with groups without an average uniform pattern of disability. Moreover, it was perceived that, while the manufactured product used consists of a massive piece of polyethylene, disallowing major changes in its structure, the DIY artefacts allow large customizations with capacity to meet individual physical requirements via a cheap material (such as glue and adhesive tape), according to the observed.

The smallest standard deviations were found in the ludic semantic group, who were asked to answer questions regarding the aesthetic and signification aspects of the pencil grips. This demonstrates the strong relation between children and subjective issues, like shapes and colors, in products of their daily lives and, therefore, the importance of the attention to this emotional aspect during the designing of these products. The A and C models, with a composite design of colored material, and also the D model, composed of a small ball, got positive

Figure 12. Graph comparing the assessments of model C, made by the participant K, which practices immature palmar gripping (holds the material with the palm, in a sensitive manner), relative to the participant R, which has a tripod grasp (makes the use of three fingers to hold), with great force of application (Kang & Ikeuchi, 1991). Source: Authors.

reviews and reactions tangent to the visual aspects, evidencing the interest and enjoyment in their use, which may have a great collaboration in infant's educational processes (Freitas, 2007). Also, it was observed that most of the models easily found on the Brazilian market were made of dark colors, such as black (like the model used this study), and gray. Thus, this information was taken into account through the process of making DIY models for use with the protocol. Using as a reference the infantile world, grounded on these exploration ideas of colors and forms (Moura, 2006), the aspect of the handmade models quoted above were based especially on these lines. And so, the smallest differences encountered in the results on this ambit, shown before, reinforce the existence of this relation.

A peculiar situation also draws attention to this ludic side, in the case of the thickener made of a little ball. Some children played more with the object that this thickener was made from, than painted the drawing — which was not to be necessarily seen as a problem at all times, since the play helps children to relate to the world and recreate situations their daily lives, and stimulates essential actions and feelings to social life (Vygotsky, 1991). Also, according to Mafra (2007), the game within the learning process provides greater autonomy to children with disabilities, improving self-esteem and body knowledge, which increases their development.

Still exists a panorama that can be explored, derived from the results of this application. In regard to industrial products, a deeper look at the creation of a bigger affinity between user and product can take place, such as including the possibility of changing parts, formats or colors of the objects. This means that the matter of a design for few people should not be neglected in any aspect — as it actually is on many occasions — and this is imbricated this scenario as well. The collabora-

tive process also could be an important tool to improve this, once the user is one of the main potential sources of information and innovation (Gaither & Fraizer, 2002) about the product that is being developed. This collaboration can be done from the initial stages of product development, like involving the potential users and people linked to the user environment (e.g. occupational therapists, caregivers, and family) in the process, and testing prototypes using models of objective and subjective evaluation (as the DS protocol), until its post-development, (e.g. making use of an active channel of communication with the client and giving incentives for user feedbacks). *Unless the developer is a disabled person, he cannot know about being a disabled person, and so, can't develop correctly a product for us, and he has to hear us* — and this sentence, heard from a disabled citizen in a research interview, briefly summarizes this importance of capturing the user experience and personal concerns.

In general, the best scores of homemade thickeners shown by the protocol were close to the evaluations of the industrial product, showing the feasibility of using these kinds of homemade devices in teaching and recreational scenarios, always according to the specificity of disability. The possibility and adequacy to a different adaptation, both in ludic and practical issues, and its low cost of production, indicates that its use should be encouraged not only in institutions (as it is already widely practiced in Brazil), but also among family members of the children, extending the practice into different types of assistive products (once the problems related to the commercial case of pencil thickeners are similar to other types of objects found in this area — like high prices, lack of variety, and attention to personal values of the user). An example of this

idea that is already being applied there is the practice of some institutions located in the big cities of Brazil, which conduct workshops with needy families about DIY assistive products.

The protocol of the semantic differential a good response about its use in assistive technology products, but special attention must be given regarding the variables of disabilities that can be found in the application context, which can generate a very wide range of responses in the questionnaires. In the case of this present study, the data about specific physical performances related to each patient was collected from the questionnaires, with the intention of making possible the conduction of a more precise check of these pencil grip evaluations in the future. A brief summary table containing the results found by the DS model follows.

Figure 13. Participant successfully using a homemade pencil thickener model. Source: Authors.

PENCIL THICKENER	INDICATED PREHENSION	POSITIVE POINTS	CRITICAL POINTS	COSTS
	Cylindrical grasp or tripod (KANG & IKEUCHI, 1991), with more gross motor coordination.	- Use of colors; - Good ludic potential; - Softness; - Moldable thickness.	- Short durability.	Under a Brazilian real.
	Cylindrical grasp or tripod grasp (KANG & IKEUCHI, 1991), with more gross motor coordination.	- Stable material.	- Not easily moldable; - Stiffness of the material; - Little ludic potential.	No cost (reused corks).
	Tripod grasp (KANG & IKEUCHI, 1991), with more gross motor coordination.	- Use of colors; - Different format; - Good ludic potential; - Moldable thickness.	- Weakness of the inner material (styrofoam);	Under a Brazilian real.
	Spherical grasp (KANG & IKEUCHI, 1991), brush grasp or jaw chuck (BERRY, 1999)	- Different format; - Good ludic potential;	- Heavy; - Little possibility of customization; - Instability; - Requires practice for better handling.	About two Brazilian reais.
	Cylindrical grasp or tripod grasp (KANG & IKEUCHI, 1991), with more gross motor coordination.	- Stable material; - Softness.	- Heavy; - Little ludic potential; - Little possibility of customization.	About 25 Brazilian reais.

Table 02. Table containing the results found by the DS protocol.

Source: Authors.

CONCLUSION

The so called *gambiarra* has a special social role in assistive technology, and even with the pejorative baggage charged by the term, in this area it is maybe a solution which is often the only affordable means of owning certain devices, in some socioeconomic contexts. In this study, the pencil grip reviews have proved the useful potential of this artifact, as an aid mechanism for the implementation of tasks, in certain cases (depending on the model and disability), with the same performance of the manufactured product, within the terms evaluated by protocol. Thus, these improvised products have the capacity to meet the everyday user's needs of this type of artefact, added to the personal and subjective value that this homemade product can bring, working the design for the emotional side of the user, and more to it: a fact of great importance, especially in view of the child user, and the fact that this facet is often denied by commercial models.

Through this complex framework, the DS evaluation model becomes a functional protocol for this kind of test, being agile and quick, capturing the most instant facets of use of a product. Promoting the view of the most subjective characteristics, this model allowed the research to notice the importance of the most ludic features of the product design used in the infant learning environment in the area of assistive technology, creating a greater affinity between the user's universe and the product, commonly not provided by most popular models in the market. Still, even with the limitations of the test due to the multiplicity of physical profiles of the study participants, it was possible through this research to achieve a visualization of this aspect linked to the emotional factor, which is very important and attached to the infant sphere.

Finally, it is expected that this research can collaborate somehow on future studies concerned with the subjective side of assistive technology in all of your means of development, whether through a DIY method, or by mass production. The opportunity of seeing and adding a personal value on these type of products is narrowly linked with wellbeing and the quality of performing daily activities. And it can be observed and improved through lots of different ways; for instance, by using evaluating methods as the DS protocol, via the collaboration of professionals immersed in the universe of the user, or by tacit acknowledgments, like the living experiences of all social actors involved in this process.

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UNIVERSIDADE FEDERAL DE SÃO CARLOS (UFSCar)
 CAMPUS SOROCABA
 PROGRAMA DE PÓS-GRADUAÇÃO EM ENGENHARIA DE PRODUÇÃO

Avaliação de percepção de produto

Nome do(a) profissional: _____ Idade: _____
 Nome do(a) paciente: _____ Idade: _____
 Deficiência: _____

Modelo: (A) (B) (C) (D) (E)

	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3	
É leve								É pesado
É estável								É instável
É comum								É diferente
É confortável								É incômodo
É seguro								É inseguro
É resistente								É frágil
É atrativo								É repulsivo
É sério								É divertido
É de uso fácil								É de uso complicado
É eficaz								É ineficaz
É bonito								É feio
É anatômico								Não é anatômico

TERMO DE CONSENTIMENTO LIVRE E ESCLARECIDO (TCLE)

Convidamos o (a) senhor(a) para participar da pesquisa **Noções perceptivas de modelos de engrossadores de lápis, através do protocolo de avaliação DS**, sob a responsabilidade da pesquisadora **Juliana Maria Moreira Soares**, a qual pretende avaliar diversos modelos de engrossadores de lápis, de acordo com suas diversas características.

Sua participação é voluntária e se dará por meio do **preenchimento de um questionário mediante o uso dos diferentes modelos de engrossadores de lápis.**

A participação nessa pesquisa não apresenta riscos físicos ou psicológicos ao participante. Aceitando participar dessa pesquisa, **estará contribuindo para os estudos no campo de tecnologia assistiva com relação à sua construção caseira e seus aspectos subjetivos com relação ao usuário.**

Se depois de consentir em sua participação o senhor (a) desistir de continuar participando, tem o direito e a liberdade de retirar seu consentimento em qualquer fase da pesquisa, seja antes ou depois da coleta dos dados, independente do motivo e sem nenhum prejuízo a sua pessoa. O (a) senhor (a) não terá nenhuma despesa e também não receberá nenhuma remuneração.

Os resultados da pesquisa serão analisados e publicados, mas sua identidade não será divulgada, sendo guardada em sigilo. Para qualquer outra informação, o (a) senhor (a) poderá entrar em contato com o pesquisador no endereço **Rua Ana Augusto, 470, ap. 101, Sorocaba – SP**, ou pelo telefone **(12) 99106 0497**.

Eu, _____, fui informado (a) sobre o que o pesquisador quer fazer e porque precisa da minha colaboração, e entendi a explicação. Por isso, eu concordo em participar do projeto, sabendo que não vou ganhar nada e que posso sair quando quiser. Este documento é emitido em duas vias que serão ambas assinadas por mim e pelo pesquisador, ficando uma via com cada um de nós.

Sorocaba, _____ de _____ de 2014

Assinatura do participante

Assinatura do Pesquisador Responsável

GENERATING POSITIVE EMOTIONS DURING DRIVING

THE PRODUCT QUALITIES OF A CAR AFFECT EMOTIONAL CONDITIONS

Sevcan Yardim

Research Assistant , Department of Industrial Design

Faculty of Fine Arts, Design and Architecture,

TOBB University of Economics and Technology

✉ syardim@etu.edu.tr

ABSTRACT

Our lives depend on mobility, and we spend much of our precious time undertaking transportation activities during our daily routines. Generally, these activities may seem like a waste of time and turn out to be self-torture. What's more, being a passenger is somehow more advantageous than being a driver, because drivers have to concentrate only on the activity of driving. Since traffic involves unexpected and unfortunate events, this stressful environment generates negative feelings. From this point of view, driving seems to be an activity generating more negative feelings than positive ones. In this framework, this study aims to find out cues about driving activity and design solutions which generate positive effects by identifying the underlying reasons and expectations of the users with regard to product qualities.

KEYWORDS: *subjective well-being, transportation technologies, positive emotions*

INTRODUCTION

Transportation is one of the major activities of our lives. Everyday we use several different transportation modes to reach our aimed destinations. It is possible to define transportation in two different ways according to the aim of the activity, one is transportation for work and the other is transportation for leisure. According to research carried out for investigating transportation modes affecting the happiness level of users, using personal cars is still the most popular way of transportation for work, even though negative emotions are mostly experienced during transportation to work, by driving personal cars (Duarte et al., 2009).

As technology enables higher speeds, travelling distances increase and the average time spent during transportation for work averages at about one hour a day per person (Lyons and Urry, 2005). It is possible to say that the time spent in transportation is a significant amount of our lives. During our transportation activities due to misfortunate, unexpected events such as congested roads, accidents, violations, and so on, sometimes it is impossible to adjust timing and to keep calm in traffic. Moreover, the driving activity is much more stressful since it necessitates personal control and attention over the events happening around you.

There are several in-vehicle technologies designed to enhance our experience within the car, since we spend an important amount of our time during driving. These technologies become a way to cope with stress caused by outer effects by assisting or even sometimes taking the control from us. Even though these applications aim to reduce stress, they generally focus on safety related problems. Furthermore, staying away from stress is not only related with support and safety, but also positively affected by personal wellbeing. Therefore, it is important to consider possible design solutions to enhance wellbeing rather than minimizing problems and enhancing safety, which needs a possibility driven design approach rather than problem driven solutions.

In relation to these arguments, this study aims to understand the relationship between subjective well-being and in-vehicle technologies, and to find ways to create positive emotions for drivers during the activity of transportation for work. In order to reach the aim, the following questions are to be answered:

- What are the product qualities of their cars that generate positive emotions during the activity of transportation to work for drivers?
- What are the expectations, expected product qualities, of drivers from their cars in the future in order to create positive emotions?

In order to gain answers, it is crucial to consult the literature and research available on transportation and positive psychology.

TRANSPORTATION AND POSITIVE PSYCHOLOGY

Scanning through transportation and positive psychology research, it is possible to identify the main research focuses, which are: stress and time relationship, urban planning, and transportation mode choice. There are studies focusing on the statistics about transportation activities from economy literature, generally focusing on the time spent and its economic results, and which shows that an average person spends about an hour per day in transportation activities (Schafer & Victor, 2000; Lyons & Urry, 2005). From an urban planning point of view:

- Reports focusing on the growing population, polarization of economic growth, rise in greenhouse gases, and decreasing transportation budgets (Falconer & Mitchell, 2012) are suggesting solutions about transportation infrastructure of a city, including intelligent communication agents.
- Studies like Schroeter & Rakotonirainy (2012) focus on the urban informatics systems and their benefits to safety by organizing an idea creation workshop with the help of fourteen Urban Informatics research experts. These workshops focus on 'enhancing social interaction between people in urban environments' (Schoeter & Rakotonirainy, 2012, p.1.), and providing this ergonomically and safely.
- Papers asking the question about the meaning of electric vehicles among people and investigating EVs through performance, interest, and meaning perceived by drivers and others (Burgess et al., 2013). Also another study is investigating if EVs have any effects on driving behaviors and encourage sustainable behaviors (Labeye et al., 2012).

At the same time there are studies about intelligent in-vehicle systems from different scopes like acceptability, adaptability, driver behavior, behavior adaptation, driver attitudes, primary and secondary tasks of driving, information load... etc.

- Bader et al., (2011) discuss if the drivers accept recommendations about later actions (proactive) while driving. A scenario has been built about gas station recommenders; selecting gas stations according to user preferences and this in-vehicle system used by fifteen volunteers and then evaluated by using TAM of Davis (1989).
- Kujala's (2009) study is about the effects of two user interface menu structures compared in a driving simulation with the measures of visual time-sharing efficiency, visual load, driving performance, and secondary task performance.
- Acceptability of ITS systems is also a question for many papers (Regan et al., 2002; Vlassenroot et al., 2010), but these papers generally focus on some of the ITS technologies, and these kind of studies are usually conducted with psychologists and engineers in cooperation.

Looking through the researches above, it is possible to see that there are studies mainly focusing on the transportation systems from a problem solving point of view. As was mentioned before, creating a more positive traffic environment can be achieved by focusing on the driver within the driving to work context. To define and understand the positive effect psychology, literature and the well-being concepts are important sources. In the following part well-being and positive effect will be defined.

What is Well-being

Well-being is a concept that is defined in several different ways, sometimes depending on personal happiness, others, seeking positive effects. It also used to be defined as the absence of suffering, but today it is much more like the relationship between positive effects and negative effects.

There are two different approaches to the concept of well-being. Forgeard et al. (2011) describes these approaches:

- Objective measures of well-being; that has objective criteria generally based on needs
- Subjective measures of well-being; not consisting of a list about needs but focusing on the individual's own conative states.

Objective well-being depends on the concept of well-being in an objective way apart from a person's own thoughts about his/her life, whereas subjective well-being depends on the person's own thoughts about his/her life. Since the study focuses on the concept of well-being at a personal level, subjective well-being will be the main focus of the study.

Subjective well-being can be summarized as 'people's cognitive and affective evaluations of their lives' (Diener, 2000, p. 34). It depends on the people's own evaluations about how their lives are. As was mentioned before, Diener (2000) also focuses on the balance between negative and positive effects in a person's life. For example, more pleasant and few unpleasant emotions, engaging activities, gives satisfaction to a person with relation to his/her life. From Diener et al.'s (1999) point of view, it is possible to identify the components of subjective well-being as;

- Pleasant Effect; joy, elation, contentment/pride, affection, happiness, ecstasy
- Unpleasant Effect; guilt and shame, sadness, anxiety and worry/anger, stress, depression, envy
- Life Satisfaction; desire to change life, satisfaction with current life, satisfaction with past, satisfaction with future, significant others' views of one's life
- Domain Satisfaction; work, family, leisure, health, finances, self, one's group (Diener et al., 1999, p.277).

During the research, the general focus point will be the pleasant effect component of subjective well-being.

METHODOLOGY

The aim of the study is to find out product qualities of a car generating positive feelings amongst drivers. In order to find out answers:

- The first step is to identify a suitable user group; the second step is to gather the demographic information of the user group; and, lastly a semi-structured interview has been conducted among suitable user groups with the help of visual materials that I prepared to stimulate emotions and experiences.

Selection of user group

The user group is identified as:

- Car owners; since the ownership has effect on subjective well-being.
- As the research focuses on the activity of transportation for work the user group will be chosen among the people who drive to and from work in their daily routine.
- The age group is identified as between 30-50 year olds; people who generally have a consistent daily routine.
- Gender is kept in equal numbers.

The interviews are carried out with eighteen users, the initial information is consisting of mostly demographic questions like;

- Age (ranged from 29-49, with a mean of $M=36,6$)
- Gender (kept equal: 9 females, 9 males)

- The average duration of the journey between home and work (ranged from 8 to 15 without traffic but rises to 45 minutes according to traffic conditions).

Interview Structure

For the last step an interview is conducted with laddering techniques. Before the interview, people are shown two mood boards that display pictures of drivers feeling positive and negative effects. These mood boards are prepared for stimulating positive and negative effects, as well as ideas and past experiences on the respondents.

- Boards are created with an online image search using the keywords obtained from Diener et al.'s (1999) Components of Subjective Well-being table, under the pleasant and unpleasant effects titles.
- Keywords; angry driver, anxious driver, contented driver, depressed driver, elated driver, envious, feeling ecstasy, feeling shame, guilty driver, happy driver, joyful driver, positive driving, proud driver, sad driver, stressful driver, worried driver. (Keywords are generally associated with the words driving or driver, but some of them were used with the word feeling, since there are no healthy images representing the feeling in a driving context.)
- In addition to images, also those keywords are used in the mood boards to clarify the exact (intended) feelings and to keep users engaged with the images more than just for a glimpse while reading the words.
- Firstly the negative emotion board has been given to the respondent.

Figure 1. Negative feelings mood board

Figure 2. Positive feelings mood board

The user is asked to look at the mood board and imagine his/her journey of the day, and then the mood board is taken away.

- Secondly the positive emotions board is given to the respondent and left in front of him/her during the interview to stimulate positive feelings.

After that point, with the help of mood boards, the interview is conducted. Since it is possible to analyze the driving experience in three phases, the interview is carried out in an activity based manner.

Figure 3. Phases of driving activity

The interview is built upon the scenario of the user's journey between home and work. To keep the time line in its normal positions, the morning journey experience to work is the first event, and the last the evening experience of returning home. The following questions are asked about the three driving phases:

- What do you experience that makes you feel much more positive while you are walking to your car/ driving your car to/from work/leaving your car behind after your journey?

- How positive do they make you feel? Why?
- Which features do you expect from your car that affect you positively?
- What else could be useful which is not available right now but may be used in the future?

RESULTS

This study has been conducted with 18 participants; aged between 29-49 with a mean of $M=36,6$, distributed evenly in both genders, and consisting of car owners driving between their homes and work in their daily routines.

Users are interviewed with laddering techniques about their daily experiences driving between their homes and work, and are ultimately asked about the expectations they have from their cars in the future to generate a more positive environment during driving to and from work.

Data Coding

The data gained by the interviews are transcribed to an Excel sheet and the data was coded under four categories:

- Affected: the feelings that are affected by the product qualities of car. Feelings are keywords obtained from Diener et al.'s (1999) Components of Subjective Well-being table under the pleasant and unpleasant effects titles.

- Requirement: the basic requirement that affects the user
- Product quality: the requirements and design features engaged with the product and qualities.
- Design features: the features that the user already uses or wants to use.

ANALYSES

As a result of the coded data, there appears to be three major driver personas related with in-vehicle requirements. What is common for all personas is the desire for ‘comfort’ related requirements, as expected. However, the second group of preferences changes from persona to persona under three titles: safety, support, and aesthetics. One third of the users are driven by comfort and support, and are named as ‘moody drivers’; one sixth of the users are driven by comfort and safety, and are named as ‘cautious drivers’; lastly one sixth of the users are driven by comfort and aesthetics, and are named ‘image oriented drivers’. It is summarized in Figure 4 by listing

requirements according to percentages of mention times by different personas.

Even though the major requirements are the same and close to each other, the interpretation of concepts differ between these groups.

As can be seen from Figure 5, Moody drivers' interpretation of comfort mostly involves the qualities of smartness and personal space in a car. They need their cars to be ready before their access, to have information about the different situations such as tire condition, damage if there is any...etc. that would interrupt their driving routines. Also they want automatization for some routine driving activities such as changing gears, accelerating...etc.. They feel the need for support during their journey when they face an unexpected, unwanted event. They are also concerned mostly about the smartness of the car, so that it is able to understand the mood of the driver and possesses smart solutions for different situations. Their third requirement is about safety, which is mostly dependent again on the smartness of the car, suggesting and applying solutions for threats to the safety of the car, and also, again, automatization for some activities.

Figure 4. User classification according to percentages of mention times of major requirements

Figure 6 is about requirement relations of cautious drivers whose major requirements are comfort and safety. Similar to moody drivers, cautious drivers' comfort is highly dependent on the smartness and personal space of the car, but their major concerns are about gaining information and automatization of some driving activities. Secondly their needs for safety also depend on the smartness of the car which involves again some warning options and automatization. What's more, production quality is another concern about safety deriving from need for different materials and visual access solutions. Lastly cautious drivers have the need for support dependent on the smart options mostly involving assistance and mood management.

As with the last group, image oriented drivers are mostly affected by comfort options and also aesthetic properties of a car. Their expectations from comfort differ from other drivers as they mostly focus on the personal space of a car that they create away from traffic during their journey. Their second requirement is about aesthetics, which is dependent on the appearance and image of the car; from color to license plate they personalize their cars and feel affection about some aesthetic properties of it. Lastly they also need support during their journey and assistance with their personal needs. Figure 7 summarizes the requirement relations of image-oriented drivers.

As can be seen from the figures, there are some similarities and differences between three groups of drivers with regards to requirements and also their interpretations of these requirements. In order to understand these properties deeper the sub requirements of the users are analyzed.

Comfort related qualities

Comfort is the most mentioned requirement by all the groups, but it refers to different kinds of needs and wants. It is mostly dependent on the qualities of smartness and personal space. Figure 8 summarizes the difference between the user group about smartness and the personal space of the car.

For smartness of the car, moody and image-oriented drivers generally want their cars to be ready before their access, organizing the in-car climate conditions and air quality. They want to enter a cozy environment with personalized settings which has an organized climate through the air and the places that they touch. Also the first impression of the car was built with an indoor smell, which evokes the feelings of an unhealthy, plastic, dirty environment, especially after sun exposure. Furthermore cautious drivers mostly focus on the information they gain about the route suggestions and organize their daily schedule around that information. Moody drivers need information not only about their daily schedule but also information about parking spots and possible bad surprises, like broken car functions that may slow them down and waste their time. Lastly all groups of drivers want smartness automatization, but for different reasons cautious drivers need automation of driving activities for safer environments, whereas moody and image-oriented drivers want it for getting rid of boredom and tiredness caused by the routine of driving activities during traffic.

Figure 6. Requirement relations of cautious drivers (according to the percentages of mention times)

Figure 5. Requirement relations of moody drivers (according to the percentages of mention times)

Figure 7. Requirement relations of image oriented drivers (according to the percentages of mention times)

Figure 8. Comfort related product qualities(according to the percentages of mention times)

Personal space of the car is another factor that affects mostly the moody and image oriented drivers and that is mostly about the cozy environment that they create during their journey, like having coffee around with the company of music and an ergonomic, relaxing, even massaging seating options. Furthermore, image-oriented drivers are oriented by their images too and need extra storage areas inside for their personal belongings, like sunglasses, wallets and spare shoes. Moreover

moody and image-oriented drivers both focus on the ease of use of the controls with understandable interfaces inside the car, but image-oriented drivers also ask for playful interactions with these controls through tactual properties during driving. Lastly cautious drivers have the need for a cozy environment, but they prefer to stay low and don't want to be distracted by these properties.

Support related qualities

Apart from comfort, overall support is the second most mentioned requirement. There are also several similar and different tendencies involved with support related product qualities that are summarized in Figure 9.

Support related qualities are highly affected by the smartness of the car. Moody drivers are the ones that need support after comfort, and they highly need mood management in cases of an unexpected, unwanted event. For moody drivers mood management depends mostly on the in-car air conditioning. When they need to cool down they actually need in-car temperature to be slightly cooler, and they also ask for the in-car air to become fresher; refreshing them and giving them the feeling of nature that could take them away from that moment. Music is important for moody and image-oriented drivers who want the smartness to understand their moods and organize

a different musical experience to revitalize or to support their mood for the day. Communication with other cars is important for moody and cautious drivers who want to express their feelings with more creative ways than claxons, which are subtle. Claxons are used for a number of different expressions, such as: thanking, anger, warning...etc.; in a mixed environment it is not easy to determine why and to whom that expression is for. This causes more stress and misunderstandings that bring the need for to-the-point and clear communication options. Assistance is also about the smartness of the car, which is needed by all the driver groups. During parking all groups need assistance for precision; to park according to comfort of the near cars, distance needed to open the doors and pedestrian comfort. Also moody and image-oriented drivers are not as careful as cautious drivers about safety precautions, so they also need assistance for the forgotten valuables, and for locking the car while leaving.

Figure 9. Support related product qualities (according to the percentages of mention times)

Figure 10. Safety related product qualities(according to the percentages of mention times)

Apart from mood management and assistance, connectivity is a major element of the smartness. Connectivity is mostly about the personal devices for moody drivers to socialize and to have the company of their friends during their journey, to complete necessary work related things, to get rid of the stress that they have, and lastly, generally during the evening journey and similarly to image-oriented drivers, to plan and organize activities from cooking and food ordering, to social activities and meeting points during their journey, as well as the ability to update their destinations. Besides, cautious drivers are mostly focusing on a wider online system to be part of legal actions about rude, dangerous drivers, and recording during driving to share with legal forces. Moody and image-oriented drivers also want

to be part of the legal actions, but moreover they want to be aware of route updates and whole traffic systems.

Safety related qualities

The third most mentioned quality is safety, which is again related with smartness and also production quality of the car. Cautious drivers are mostly focusing on the safety related qualities and the relations are summarized in Figure 10.

Cautious drivers want to be warned about outer effects during driving since as well as inner distractions, like music, there are also outer distraction, like noise, claxons...etc. They have a need to be aware of the outer events but also they don't want

to be interrupted by too many noises and the smells from traffic, so they close their windows for some isolation. In that case they want their cars to be aware and warn them about outer events, close drivers, emergency vehicles...etc. Also they feel anxiety about the safety of their cars out of their sights, which is shared by moody and image-oriented drivers too. The alarm options are no solution for their anxiety because sometimes it is not possible to hear these sounds. Also the intruder runs away when the alarm rings, which makes it impossible to catch them. They need a more personalized system that reaches to their communication devices; or even the key of the car can be an alarm option. Automatization is also mentioned during comfort options, since the drivers want to leave the control to the car and relax in case of safety, fatigue, or even boredom. From a safety point of view, the way the users want automatization changes from driver to driver. Moody drivers do not want the automatization to interrupt their driving flows; they need it to be subtle and invisible. At the same time, like cautious drivers, they want automatization to be coaching, supporting learning processes for new starters and decision making in case of an inevitable accident that distracts and stresses the driver and affects the decision making process.

Lastly, the production quality is engaged with safety options, with cautious drivers mostly focusing on the visual access options of their cars. As climate changes cause distortions in visual access they ask for a easy cleaning, self cleaning material that won't distract them during their journey with visual access areas like mirrors and glass areas. Also, the durability of the materials in case of an unwanted incident evokes trust in all of the driver groups towards their cars, which bring them contentment and pride.

Apart from these qualities, aesthetics is highly important for image driven drivers. They want to feel special with certain qualities of their cars. Aesthetics is mostly related with the appearance and image of the car, which is affected by an intimidating look created by a higher and aggressive design of the car. They also look for a unique color that is not easy to find, or the color used in the commercials while launching a new model. Another important requirement is also about self-cleaning materials; apart from safety it is mostly about the appearance of the car. Image-oriented drivers feel pride and happiness while approaching their cars and they want to see a cleaner outlook. Moreover, when they reach their cars they want to touch cleaner surfaces designed in a way that is not affected by the outer effects. Lastly some of the drivers mentioned the possibility of personalizing license plates with letters and numbers. They have a need for personalization options, such as license plates or a unique color, which can be a clue for design solutions involving personalization options.

DISCUSSION

There are several requirements that are mentioned during the study by the drivers. As can be expected, comfort is the most mentioned requirement for feeling positive effects, but there

are three different tendencies that the study revealed according to the mention times of the second major requirement, and the drivers grouped under three groups such as moody, image-oriented, and cautious drivers.

Scanning through the product qualities related with the requirements of all groups the major factor can be identified as the smartness that is related with nearly all the requirements. As the technology develops day by day, it also gets into every corner of our lives, maintaining our comfort and supporting us. Also the driving experience becomes richer with the technological developments and smart applications day by day. As a result the expectations of the drivers depend more on the smart options. Moreover, as the communication devices become mobile, they become our main companion in every aspect of our lives. Therefore connectivity creates a higher demand. In this study this is mostly about personal devices but for the future connectivity will become crucial for designing a whole transportation system that is aware of every other device around.

Apart from smartness, drivers have a need for creating an in-car environment away from traffic, which is highly related with the personal space of the car, which used to be defined as the interior design of the car, but nowadays is more dependent on the technological advances that support the comfort of the drivers. That also involves smartness in a way that realizes the driver's condition and offers personalized options for different drivers; like massaging and adapting seating and playful driving activities. Even the musical experience involves technological advances around personalization and sound quality.

Also, the production quality of the car is highly engaged with the safety precautions, and is again dependent on the technological advances about materials that in a way involve smartness, like self-cleaning or adjusting according to external effects. Durability of the materials also evokes trust in the car, and enables drivers to feel pride and contentment.

Lastly, the study reveals the close relationship between comfort, support, safety, aesthetic options, and feeling positive, but also shows the close relationship between requirements and technological advances. All of these requirements are musts, but the importance levels change according to user groups.

FURTHER STUDIES

The study revealed three groups of users distinguished from each other according to their main requirements for feeling positive effect in the driving context. There are some similarities and differences between the product qualities they associate with their requirements. Moreover there are some similarities and differences while interpreting product qualities, but their most important common point is technological advances and the concept of smartness. The study revealed that the requirements of the drivers mostly depended on technological advances, and even though it is interpreted differently, the smartness of the car from different points of view.

For further studies the relationship between technology and requirements will be interpreted through the identification of user and technology relationship.

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BIOPHILIC DESIGN + POSITIVE DESIGN = VITAL DESIGN DESIGNING TO COMPREHENSIVELY SUPPORT USER WELLBEING

Sally Augustin, PhD
Design With Science
✉ sallyaugustin@designwithscience.com

ABSTRACT

Biophilic design leads to the development of places and objects that humans find beautiful and that generate a positive affect. Beautiful places and things endure because they are comforting, pleasing, and satisfying – aesthetically, emotionally, and, as required, functionally. Beauty is not just in the eyes of the beholders, and the development of beautiful places and objects can be informed by research in the social and physical sciences. Positive design leads to the creation of places and objects that directly enhance subjective wellbeing. They are tailored to the psychological profile, aspirations, and objectives of users. When designers incorporate principles of both biophilic and positive design into their projects, the vital design solutions generated resonate with users and are environmentally sustainable; they satisfy a wider range of user needs than either biophilic or positive design solutions. Field research will link biophilic design and positive design with vital design products that enhance user welfare.

KEYWORDS: *biophilic design, positive design, positive affect, subjective wellbeing, environmental/object design.*

INTRODUCTION

Developed societies must resolve several important challenges to ensure their continued viability. First, environmental responsibility is necessary to preserve quality of life, and, ultimately, life itself. Second, creating personally meaningful experiences for citizens is also imperative (Inglehart, 2000). As Hassenzahl, Eckoldt, Diefenbach, Laschke, Lenz, and Kim state, “While society changes its focus from ‘well-fare’ to ‘wellbeing’, design becomes increasingly interested in the question of whether it can design for happiness” (2013, p.21). Biophilic design directly supports resolution of the first challenge and positive design the second by enhancing subjective wellbeing (Kellert, 2012; Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013). When biophilic design and positive design are consciously combined, in a process that can be categorized as vital design, the resulting design products are both meaningful and sustainable, and society as a whole, as well as individuals and smaller groups, benefit because critical needs at all levels of scale are recognized and satisfied. User needs from each step of Maslow’s hierarchy, from physiological to security to social to self esteem to self-actualization (Koltko-Rivera, 2006) can be fully satisfied via vital design.

Both biophilic design and positive design can generate positive affect (Kellert, 2008; Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013) and it is therefore logical that vital design can do so also. Positive affect has been linked to broadened thinking/attention and thought-action repertoires, when compared to neutral or negative state processing (Fredrickson & Branigan, 2005). In general, positive affect has been positively related to: improved creative performance and increased innovation (Isen, Johnson, Mertz, & Robinson, 1985); improved problem solving and decision making (Isen, 2001); more flexible, thorough, and efficient thinking on topics meaningful or interesting to the thinker (Isen, 2001); strategic thinking (Loken, 2006); constructive and cooperative bargaining, increased generosity, social responsibility, helping and interpersonal understanding (Isen, 2001); constructive suggestions (George & Brief, 1992); avoidance of real and meaningful risk (Isen, Johnson, Mertz, & Robinson, 1985); and improved self-knowledge (Fredrickson, 2001). Positive emotions can help build durable personal resources such as physical skills or health, social resources such as friendships and networks, intellectual resources such as knowledge, and psychological resources such as optimism (Fredrickson & Branigan, 2005).

BIOPHILIC DESIGN

Kellert defines biophilia as “the inherent inclination to affiliate with the natural world instrumental to people’s physical and mental health, productivity, and wellbeing”, while biophilicly designed structures reflect the essential qualities of spaces found in nature, without necessarily being precise replications of natural places (Kellert, 2012, p. xii). Biophilicly designed areas “are designed in ways that foster people’s physical and mental health through providing positive connections to nature in a context of ecological and cultural meaning” (Kellert, 2012, p. 158).

Denis Dutton delineated the link between beauty and biophilic design (2009). His work makes it clear that biophilic design leads to the development of spaces and objects that humans consider beautiful, regardless of their culture of origin. Dutton traces the apparently universal associations between biophilic design and beauty to the Pleistocene environments in which humans reached roughly their current state of evolutionary development, physically and socially. Dutton’s position is that we consider certain aspects of nature beautiful today because the same elements, during the Pleistocene era, supported our survival; for example, by helping us escape from predators.

Dutton details how across the planet people find the same sort of landscapes beautiful and illustrates his claim by referring to the Hudson River school of painting. These paintings and locations share certain attributes. They have a view out over stretches of grassy fields with occasional groups of trees (preferably with forks near the ground). Water is either directly in view or inferred in the distances and a trail we could walk, because it is a path or shoreline or riverbank, invites us to enter the scene and move through it among other animals and birds. Similar examples are provided of biophilic objects, such as ancient ax heads, although research has focused on biophilicly designed spaces. Those aspects of nature found beautiful have been studied, and their underlying “design principles” identified. Those design principles form the basis of biophilic design and will be enumerated in the paragraphs that follow.

When spaces or objects are developed using biophilic design principles, they are preferred to non-biophilic alternatives and people feel very comfortable in them or while using them (Kellert, 2012). As a result, their users generally think broadly, with all of the benefits noted above. Being in a beautiful, biophilicly designed space enhances positive affect (Kellert, 2012), while beautiful objects are perceived to work better, be easier to work with, and more straightforward to figure out (Fogg, Soohoo, Anielson, Marable, Stanford, & Tauber, 2003). Beauty, in short, is functional as well as preferred.

Kellert directly links biophilic design and the experience of beauty with environmentally sustainable behavior (2012, p.162). As he states:

Ultimately, low-impact design fails to achieve its goal of sustainability, because it falls short of nurturing the physical and mental benefits that create the emotional and

intellectual attachment that motivates people to be good stewards of their constructions and to retain them over the long term... As the architect James Wines suggested: ‘People will never want to keep an aesthetically inferior building around, no matter how well stocked with cutting edge thermal glass, photovoltaic cells, recycled materials, and zero-emissions carpeting’.

Hosey makes a similar point, “As studies show, we form positive associations with things we consider beautiful, we are more likely to become emotionally attached, giving them pet names, for instance. We personalize things we care about... people generally consider attractive products more functional than they do unsightly ones and therefore are more apt to use them. We prefer using things that look better, even if they aren’t inherently easier to use. Consider the ramifications—if an object is more likely to be used, it’s more likely to continue being used. Who throws out a thing they find functional, beautiful, and valuable all at once? A more attractive design discourages us from abandoning it: if we want it, we won’t waste it” (2012, p. 7). In addition, “we also take better care of such [attractive] environments, which tend to have less litter, waste, and vandalism” (2012, p. 26).

Kellert identifies signature principles of biophilic design (2008). They include:

- Using natural elements, from materials to sunlight and fresh air to plants.
- Including natural shapes, generally curvilinear.
- Creating the same sort of sensory experiences found in nature by, for example, actively considering the full range of sensations that people will experience, e.g., place/product related scents, textures touched, etc. Ideally, these should vary with time, as experiences in nature are different at various times of the day and year, or in response to more random events, such as a thunderstorm. Some materials change over longer periods of time, for example, as they age and develop a patina.
- Developing links between spaces/objects being designed and the physical and cultural environments where they will be used.
- Utilizing visual fractals with specific parameters, as outlined in a paragraph to follow.
- Integrating humans in ways that make them feel safe and confident. We feel secure when we’re not concerned about being approached from the rear without our knowledge and when we can survey the world around us from a protected position (this is known as having “prospect and refuge”), for example.
- Generating the same experience of spaciousness found in natural settings while clearly delineating individual territories (when spaces are designed).

Heerwagen and Gregory (2008) build on the basic tenets of biophilic design presented by Kellert (2008). They propose creating ‘a new palette for design’ that has, in addition to the biophilic elements identified by Kellert:

- Gentle, repetitive, rhythmic motion, like that of grasses in a meadow moving in a slight breeze.
- Pleasant but not totally predictable encounters/experiences. These might be, for example, at a variety of scales, one at standing height and another when people are seated and explore an object at closer range. Building ornamentation can vary in appearance as light illuminates it in different ways, leading to unexpected, but pleasant, experiences. Unanticipated positive experiences are rewards for sensory exploration.
- Flexible use options. When we're outside in natural settings, we have multiple possibilities for what to do next, and spaces and objects can also support flexibility, spontaneity, and a range of activities. Flexibility is closely related to 'freeness' in an environment and strategically placed sight lines that provide expansive views as well as openable windows that can be opened promote 'freeness'.

Judith Heerwagen (2009) discusses several additional attributes of biophilic design. She proposes using simulated (via photographs or other means) natural elements (i.e., views and plants), when real ones are not an option. She also recommends creating spaces/objects that are as complex visually, acoustically, etc., as natural ones to optimize the level of sensory inputs received by people.

Joye (2007) finds that biophilic design enhance humans' emotional and cognitive performance, and discusses additional attributes of biophilic architectural/interior design, recommending:

- Varying architectural topography.
- Including water features, or when possible, small fires in spaces developed.
- Repeating design elements through patterns in tiling, mosaics, stained glass, and oriental carpets.
- Bending a hallway or corridor slightly, so that there is some mystery surrounding what may lie around the corner. Too much mystery can be confusing, but levels of mystery can be moderated by views to the outside or a more regular building shape.

Joye notes that many different styles of popular architecture display details at different scales, mimicking to some extent fractal patterns.

Research, only some of which can be presented here, supports the biophilic design recommendations made by Kellert, Heerwagen, Joye, and others and highlights their positive implications for mood and the related matters of preference and performance.

- In a comprehensive assessment of the literature, Browning and his team found that biophilic architectural/interior design is linked to greater professional productivity, enhanced mental health and wellbeing, and better financial performance at stores and corporations; improved health of hospital patients; and expedited learning rates for students (Browning et al., 2012).
- Research consistently finds that when people experience visual or acoustic fractal patterns similar to those found in nature they become more relaxed and their mood improves (Wise, 2002). In all fractals, the components of a pattern appear at various magnifications within the same overall unit. For example, the smallest visible components of ferns have the same basic form as entire fern leaves. As Wise reports, the experience of natural fractals has been shown to speed recovery from surgery and to increase office worker productivity. Research in knowledge-worker offices has found that the use of visible natural fractals in an environment can improve memory while reducing stress and keeping cognitive performance from deteriorating over time (Wise, 2002). Warmuth and Joseph have found that the sound of indoor waterfalls, which is a natural acoustic fractal, significantly reduces the systolic blood pressure of people with dementia (2008). Higher levels of systolic blood pressure speeds cognitive decline. A literature review revealed that humans seem to prefer and are most comfortable when fractal patterns have values of 1.3 to 1.5, and people judge these fractals most aesthetically pleasing (Joye, 2007). These are the same values observed in fractals found in biophilic environments (Wise & Hazzard, 2002).
- The optimal scale of visual patterns for wallpapers, etc., seems to be one in which it's relatively easy to pick out potentially dangerous elements; smaller scale ones are preferred to larger (Rodemann, 1999).
- Humans register their highest levels of environmental satisfaction—and higher levels of environmental satisfaction have been linked to superior professional performance—in places with moderate visual complexity and similarly prefer to look at scene/artwork with moderate visual complexity (Kaplan, 1987; Forsythe, Nadal, Sheehy, Cela-Conde & Sawey, 2011). It is easy to spot predators against such patterns (Wise & Hazzard, 2002).
- Seeing wood grain is a natural de-stressor (Fell, 2010). This information is particularly important because wooden objects and finishes can be used in any sort of space (e.g., schools, hospitals, offices)—for example ones without views of nature, or ones that cannot support plants.
- Symmetrical stimuli (objects, patterns, etc.) are preferred and generally found to be beautiful, and in nature healthy living things are generally symmetrical (Lindell & Mueller, 2011; Chen, Wu, & Wu, 2011). Open and symmetrical spaces are categorized as more beautiful than any others (Ellard, 2009).
- Sunlight varies in color through the course of any day, and Knoop has identified benefits of varying the colors of artificial light used inside during the day (2007). Warm light is best when people prefer to relax and cooler light is better when people need to be alert. Sunlight at noon is a cooler color and at sunset is a warmer color.
- When we don't have access to daylight, which not only changes in color but also in intensity during the day, we become tense and under-stimulated (Veitch & Galasiu, 2012).

- Natural objects tend to be more curvilinear and research has shown that people prefer objects that are curved and feel calmer, in better moods, and more comfortable in spaces where curved elements predominate (Bar & Neta, 2007; Dazkir & Read, 2012; Vartanian et al., 2013).
- When investigating preferred seats in restaurants, Robson learned that the locations where people experience the most positive moods are those where there is something significant, such as a wall, column, partition, or large plant, for example, behind the seated patron, which impedes the approach of potentially troublesome others (2008).
- While studying preferred design for sleeping areas, Sporle and Stich found that people prefer to sleep in a location from which they can see the entrance to the space where they're sleeping and are as far as possible from that door (2010). They also want their bed to be positioned so that it is hidden from view when the door to their sleeping area is opened.
- In urban spaces, bodies of water are perceived to be more beautiful if they are wider and if there is vegetation along their banks (Steinwender, Gundacker, & Wittmann, 2008). Artificial (hard) bank modifications seem to make bodies of water less attractive.
- Ulrich and Gilpin (2003) have determined that figurative art in healthcare settings with the following attributes enhances the likelihood of healing: green landscapes (or flowers in gardens) with an open foreground; clusters of broad canopy trees; and calm, non-threatening water elements. Abstract images should be avoided or there will be negative effects on healing. Images of threatening situations (such as extreme weather or dangerous animals) also have a deleterious effect on healing.

Biophilic design has been linked to enhanced mood, which has desirable implications for emotional, cognitive, and social performance, as detailed above. Biophilic design also has been tied to the creation of spaces and objects that are judged beautiful and that are preferred.

POSITIVE DESIGN

Desmet and Pohlmeier (2013, p. 8-9) define: “‘positive design’ as an umbrella term for all forms of design, design research and design intention in which explicit attention is paid to the effects of design on the subjective well-being of individuals and communities.... Positive design initiatives deliberately intend to increase people’s subjective well-being and, hence, increase an enduring appreciation of their lives. It is important to note that this target is the explicit central objective at the outset of a positive design process, not simply a fortunate side effect of a design.” Desmet and Pohlmeier also acknowledge that, “positive design does not deny the place of loss, failure, and negative emotions in the richness of life experiences” (2013, p. 16). Its primary purpose is to increase the likelihood that humans flourish.

Positive design, as described by Desmet and Pohlmeier, has three major components: pleasure, personal significance, and virtue (2013). When all three are present users are more likely to flourish (although all need not be present to the same degree for the effect to be found). Each element must be tailored to the psychological profile, aspirations, and objectives of anticipated users to promote flourishing.

- Pleasurable design enhances happiness at the moment of experience. This positive design objective is consistent with those of biophilic design, although biophilic design supports user comfort and security at a fundamental level and is linked only peripherally to instantaneous pleasure.
- Design for personal significance “addresses happiness that comes from a sense of personal meaning. The focus is not on momentary affect, but on one’s personal (long- or short-term) goals and aspirations” (p. 9).
- Design for virtue; “for example, eyeglasses can facilitate reading and learning (i.e., the virtues of knowledge and wisdom)” (p. 9). Both goals and virtue are achieved through individual effort. Both designing for personal significance and designing for virtue are not recognized by biophilic design, although biophilic design is environmentally responsible.

Augustin has similarly described design that enhances well-being as having five attributes (2009). It

- Comforts by providing desirable and pleasant sensory experiences.
- Communicates by sending desired messages about users to others as well as to themselves and, in general, supports social interaction.
- Complies by helping users achieve their performance objectives.
- Challenges by facilitating the development of users in ways they find meaningful.
- Continues by remaining available to users over an extended period of time, which is pleasurable and comforting.

Jordan (2000) has designated four types of pleasure that can be derived from products (drawing on the work of Lionel Tiger), and these align with the tenets of positive design as described by Desmet and Pohlmeier (2013). The evidence Jordan presents confirming the four types of pleasure he delineates validates the positive design approach. The types of pleasure discussed by Jordan are:

- Physio-pleasure – “pleasures derived from the sensory organs” (p. 13).
- Socio-pleasure – “derived from relationships with others”, both those known to the user and ‘society as a whole’ (p. 13).
- Psycho-pleasure – “pertains to people’s cognitive and emotional reactions... this might include issues relating to the cognitive demands of using the product and the emotional reactions engendered through experiencing the product” (p. 14).

- Ideo-pleasure – “pertains to people’s values.... For example, a product made from bio-degradable materials might be seen as embodying the value of environmental responsibility. This, then, would be a potential source of ideopleasure to those who are particularly concerned about environmental issues” (p. 14).

Positive design has a strong foundation in both practice and theory, as described above. It is more tightly linked to individual experiences with spaces and objects, and less to generalized ones, than biophilic design.

BIOPHILIC DESIGN, POSITIVE DESIGN, VITAL DESIGN

When biophilic design and positive design principles are simultaneously applied, the design products generated provide psychological support to users at multiple levels and vital design ensues. Biophilic design sustains users by focusing on their continuing requirements for physical comfort and safety. While positive design attends to momentary satisfaction of psychological needs at multiple levels of Maslow’s hierarchy of needs (Koltko-Rivera, 2006), it excels at supporting those at a higher level, by considering personal meaning and virtue, for example. Vital design therefore satisfies user needs at each step of Maslow’s pyramid, both instantaneously and continuously; something neither biophilic design, positive design, nor design in general does well.

A program spontaneously undertaken by an employer, without input from the researcher, illustrates how vitally designed spaces can develop, and their value to users. Forty workers at an advertising agency in North America were each given \$300 by their employer for enhancements to their workplace cubicles. The changes that these naïve designers made were consistent with vital design. The researcher interviewed these workers after they modified their workplaces (the only access acceptable to the employing organization was via interviews) and the data collected indicated that after modifying the design of their workspaces, the workers felt more committed to their employer organization than they had beforehand. Study participants also felt that after modifying their workspaces they enjoyed their time at work more and spent more time in their workplace than they had previously. Finally, they believed that they performed their professional responsibilities better in the modified workspaces than in the original ones. These perceived changes in job performance, etc., are consistent with more positive affect and higher levels of subjective wellbeing (see the first section of this paper for more information on mood, wellbeing, and performance, etc.). Also, consistent with biophilic design-related research, none of the individuals interviewed wished to make any significant changes to the design of their workspaces even six months after the cubicles were modified. All planned changes were minor, for example, re-arranging furniture already brought to the workspace from home.

All of the workers who had the opportunity to enhance their workspaces chose to do so. In addition, they were all active-

ly involved in the design and implementation process. This active control over their experiences no doubt contributed to their apparent increased happiness: “Through the deliberate and active engagement with the world, people can—at least to some degree—take control over their experiences and, thus, make themselves more (or less) happy” (Hassenzehl et al., 2013, p. 21).

Many of the workspace enhancements were clearly biophilic. For example, living plants were popular additions to workplaces as were plant and other natural materials. Workers often re-oriented their desks/seats to face the entrance to cubicles. When this was not possible for structural reasons, several employees placed large mirrors so that they had excellent views of the entrance to their cubicles. These modifications created true or pseudo ‘protected back’ positions. Several individuals hung objects overhead that moved gently in currents created by the air conditioning system. Cubicle re-designs were generally multi-sensory and invited exploration. Spaces developed also had many curved elements and could often be used in a variety of ways (e.g., cubicles now contained reconfigurable work areas).

Also in line with biophilic design principles, individuals created clearly delineated territories that they alone could claim. Boundaries were established via several methods, including the addition of rugs that indicated the extent of floor space belonging to a particular individual as well as the addition of a plaster-like material to the inside surfaces of some cubicle walls to make the cubicles themselves seem more substantial. Some workers added doors—swinging on hinges or made from bead curtains—to their cubicles. One enterprising individual added a doorbell to their cubicle as a way to signal availability—if she did not answer the doorbell, she was not available for discussion. Others indicated their availability via flag-based signal systems. In one case, a territory was established via a scent; the amount of scent dispensed into the air by a finely tuned mechanical system spread to the edge of a cubicle territory and no further.

Each cubicle, after its transformation, contained elements that clearly linked it to a single individual. Often the style/assortment of objects and decorative motifs used to customize the cubicle were described as similar to those found in the cubicle owner’s living room at home. As the work of Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton has shown, residents use the design of their living rooms to signal important qualities of their self to themselves and others (1981). Personalizing elements included an extensive collection of cartoon figurines, personal photographs, and artwork created by relatives, for example.

Many of the design elements, such as the scents and plants added to spaces, were presented as ways to enhance the momentary experience of being in a place, which is consistent with positive design.

Most of the workplace enhancements that the users developed were introduced to achieve workplace performance goals and to augment virtue by increasing wisdom/knowledge/skill. For example, one individual eliminated the desk

from his cubicle so that he could sit on the floor and work because he felt that he thought more clearly and did better work when seated cross-legged on the floor than he did while seated in a traditional desk-type chair. Other goals were more immediate and mercenary, for example, selling paintings done by a son.

Some of the modifications made to the work environments were clearly and singly linked to being virtuous. For example, one employee developed displays to facilitate bonding with African tribes people and self-identified as a benevolent world citizen. Other space enhancements were tied to religion/spirituality, such as large Christian crosses. Certain changes related to the virtue of bonding with colleagues; most of the re-fashioned cubicles had candy dishes containing sweets for visitors.

Some of the cubicle modifications focused on one or two of the three positive design components, but none of the changes made seemed to have negative repercussions for the attainment of components not specifically focused upon. Consistent with positive design, each worker created a space that they enjoyed being in and from which they could improve their world, at multiple levels.

Employees of the North American advertising agency that is the subject of this field of research were not trained architects or interior designers. They modified their workspaces, applying principles of both biophilic design and positive design, and created spaces that were environmentally sustainable. These spaces were also personally meaningful and consistent with efforts to achieve personal goals and live virtuous lives. The spaces created are vital areas, supporting the present and future wellbeing of both their users and their society.

CONCLUSION

Biophilic design and positive design enhance positive affect and subjective wellbeing, which, as detailed in the first section of this paper, has personal and societal benefits. Biophilic design leads to the development of beautiful objects/spaces and environmentally responsible lifestyles. These objects/spaces may not, however, be personally meaningful and enrich individual lives. Positive design leads to pleasurable experiences that resonate with individual goals and supports being virtuous in ways that are significant to users, but may not provide the long-term comfort of biophilically designed objects/spaces. In addition, virtues championed may not be related to environmentally responsible behavior. Neither biophilic design nor positive design alone leads to the creation of places/objects that fully satisfy individual and societal needs on a continuing basis and at all levels of Maslow's hierarchy of needs (Koltko-Rivera, 2006). Biophilic design and positive design can therefore stimulate and enhance each other and when applied together encourage subjective wellbeing. Applying both approaches to design simultaneously leads to vital design products that enrich individual and societal wellbeing.

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SUSTAINABLE TENANCIES PROGRAM

DESIGN FOR WELLBEING IN PUBLIC HOUSING, NSW- AUSTRALIA

Olga Camacho Duarte
Research Fellow, Designing Out Crime Research Centre,
Faculty of Design, Architecture and Building, University of Technology, Sydney
✉ olga.camachoduarte@uts.edu.au

ABSTRACT

Australia's housing authorities experience great challenges in managing social housing. In response, they have explored innovative service delivery approaches to enhance tenants' well-being. This paper presents two examples of social designs for tenancy management in public housing. The first, known as 'Sustainable Tenancies' program, is a one year project to reduce arrears among tenants with complex needs — conducted by a housing authority. The second example is an alternative reframing exercise based on Sustainable Tenancies and developed by the Designing Out Crime Centre (DOC). We used qualitative interviews and document analysis to evaluate the program. Subsequently, we applied Dorst's (2013) the 'Frame Creation' model of innovation to generate an alternative design to the program. The 'Sustainable Tenancies' evaluation revealed elements with potential for positive design of services in public housing. The alternative design highlighted the usefulness of reframing in providing fruitful new perspectives contributing to sustaining tenancies and increasing well-being for tenants.

KEYWORDS: *social sustainability, well-being, public housing, design, human values*

INTRODUCTION

Government agencies in New South Wales (NSW), Australia tend to favour the use of top down approaches in the implementation of social programs. These programs are often conceived under the mindset of government efficiency designed around existing bureaucratic boundaries. Social programs tend to operate with the expectation of changing patterns of behaviour influenced by the behavioural sciences. However, such approaches have been changing. While some social programs are adopting the 'libertarian paternalism approach' (Jones et. al., 2011), others are shifting their focus to achieve a deeper understanding of experiences, meanings, core human values, and well-being (Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013). A focus on the end users of services is now seen as adding value to these programs. With different levels of success, government agencies have increased their partnerships with local groups and NGO's to add a bottom up approach to program implementation.

Bottom up approaches require a human centred focus to capture the psychological aspects playing a role in such programs. In particular, human services including housing are immersed in emotionally charged contexts. Empathy, sense of pride, sense of belonging, autonomy, and connection are core

values that bring up emotions in everyday practices associated to tenancy management in public housing. Despite that, existing services tend to still operate in pragmatic and rational ways. This paper explores concepts of positive design and subjective well-being in the context of tenancy management in public housing, which investigates values and interests of the end users.

This paper presents an example of a program that was conceived in a top down approach and an alternative design based on the values of the groups involved in that program at the community level. After a brief review of relevant concepts and the context of social housing, this paper presents the Sustainable Tenancies Program, implemented to reduce arrears in one public housing estate located in NSW, Australia during 2013. Subsequently, we present an alternative design based on the lessons learnt from this program and conceived following a model known as Frame Creation that addresses design innovation, in this case, for social housing.

PUBLIC HOUSING AND SUSTAINABLE TENANCIES

The notion of public housing in Australia is emotionally charged and its residents are often misrepresented by the

media in negative ways. There is a view in some sectors of society that their poverty is a result of laziness, lack of effort, and lack of self-determination (Atkinson & Jacobs, 2008). Sensational media stories exploit opportunities to expose abuses to the welfare system and criminal behaviours when they are associated with public housing tenants, despite the fact that such cases are negligible (Walsh & Marston, 2010). Housing authorities are often perceived as negligent and are blamed for poor management of properties and housing tenants. There is a perception (reinforced by the media) that they enable negative behaviours such as vandalism due to inaction, or that they support ‘undeserving’ tenants (e.g. welfare cheats). The stigma towards public housing tenants and housing authorities makes tenancy management difficult and positive attitudes towards living in public housing uncommon.

Public housing was created to offer temporary accommodation to working class populations in times of recession. Today, their client base includes tenant groups who have lived in public housing for generations, receive government pensions, experience chronic unemployment, and have low educational attainment. In addition, mental health problems, family violence, and various types of disability are experienced by a proportion of tenants (Australian Institute of Health and Welfare, 2010).

With a few exceptions, the housing estates in NSW were built around the 1970s on the fringes of cities. Since then, they have remained isolated from the metropolitan areas with poor access to public transport, employment centres, and other amenities. The housing stock has also aged considerably and that makes property management increasingly more complex and expensive. Additionally, the decreasing government funding and the increasing demand for housing, in particular for the most vulnerable, has strengthened the difficult conditions in which Housing NSW operates.

In the past years funding has been injected into key public housing areas for community development programs (Randolph & Judd, 2000). These programs encourage collaborations and the formation of partnerships that contribute to an environment of familiarity, greater communication, and better understanding of, and between, key stakeholders (Camacho Duarte, 2013). Community development programs tend to enhance tenancy management and some districts are trying to integrate the lessons from such programs into their core business.

Housing NSW is the State government’s agency in charge of allocating social housing and managing. Housing NSW is structured around geographical districts comprising a collection of suburbs. Each District has operational teams with a leader that supervises a number of client service officers or CSO’s; and each CSO has a portfolio of about 400 properties (Family and Community Services Annual Report, 2012). Project officers, managers, and executives support operational teams. The core tenancy management tasks are: arrears, nuisance and annoyance, property care, and tenant damages. While the majority of tenants fulfil their obligations, there are small numbers that do not comply. In the suburbs where the Sustainable Tenancies program was implemented, the proportion

of tenants who fall behind their rent is around 10%. Tenants in this group were invited to participate in this program. The following section briefly reviews design frameworks and methods that have been used in this study.

CONCEPTS AND METHODS FOR SOCIAL DESIGN

Behavioural sciences have been central in the development of public service programs (Jones et al., 2011); for example, the UK and Australia have used elements of nudge theory. This theory notes that there are two systems of human thought: the automatic, which is instinctive, and the reflective, which is deliberate and self-conscious. Nudge theory claims that by altering the context of the decision, the instinctive response can be ‘nudged’ to stimulate ‘better choices’; e.g. eating healthier or drinking less alcohol (Jones et al., 2011). Furthermore, a new area of design that has the specific purpose of creating products, services, and processes that contribute to the achievement of meaning, fulfilment, and ultimately happiness, is positive design (Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013). Studies on happiness concentrate on the idea of subjective well-being; Eid and Diener (2004) define subjective well-being as ‘one’s multi-dimensional evaluation of their lives, including cognitive judgements of life satisfaction as well as affective evaluation of moods and emotions’. The multi-dimensional character of subjective well-being is becoming the focus of design researchers in the field of positive design.

Desmet & Pohlmeier (2013) note that the multi-dimensional character of subjective well-being makes it difficult to compare or measure design explorations in this field. To address this issue they have developed the ‘Framework for Positive Design’ in which they define a triad of components of subjective well-being forming this framework. These three elements are: 1) design for pleasure (experiencing positive affect); 2) design for virtue (being morally a good person); and 3) design for personal significance (pursuing personal goals) (Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013). There have been various models developed to address the design of pleasurable experiences, particularly in product design and interaction design (Desmet, 2012). Furthermore, scholars in the field of economics have studied approaches to measure personal significance and use these in indicators of prosperity that are not based on wealth, but on what people are able to do with their resources (Nussbaum, 2000). Design for virtue addresses the idea that subjective well-being increases when one exercises a virtuous behaviour aiming for altruism or philanthropy. Positive design requires that these three elements are addressed at some level but not necessarily all at the same level. Desmet and Pohlmeier (2013) also highlight that the Framework for Positive Design aims to promote a way of designing that addresses possibility-driven design, harmony and balance, personal fit, active user involvement, and long-term impact.

Similarly, Dorst (2013) uses elements of positive design, pleasure, meaning, significance, and virtue in the Frame Creation approach to innovation. This approach is a process of ideation based on the analysis of a complex problem, and the

identification of relevant stakeholders, their objectives, needs and aspirations. It involves a process of synthesis that reveals themes based on human needs and desires that are the foundation for the development of conceptual frames and design explorations. Human-centred design is one of the main principles in Frame Creation. This analysis not only focuses on end users (of products, services or spaces), but also on the requirements of the larger network of stakeholders involved in the design, maintenance, and operations related to the problem in question. Frame Creation has two main parts: one that deals with analysing the existing conditions around a problem, and the second one involves a 'creative leap' to envision positive new approaches to the problem. Eliciting emotional personal meanings through metaphors, stories, and anecdotes is an important part of this process. The frames that result from this ideation come from in-depth reflection on core human values, which are universal, and emotional experience that is subjective (Dorst, 2013).

This Frame Creation process is designed to engage not only designers but also stakeholders who have a deeper understanding of the complexities surrounding design problems. In this paper I analyse the Sustainable Tenancies Program; subsequently I use the Frame Creation process (Dorst, 2013) to explore themes and frames for alternative designs based on the program; finally I use Framework for Positive Design (Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013) to analyse the emerging frames more in-depth.

Close to the completion of this program, an evaluation was commissioned by the housing authority between September and December 2013. The evaluation aimed to review its progress and identify the social impact of the program. This paper uses data and findings from the evaluation to describe and analyse the program as it was implemented. Then, using data from the evaluation, the author and other staff from the Designing Out Crime Centre conducted a Frame Creation workshop to analyse the context, the stakeholder's values, and generate an alternative approach to this program. The alternative approach developed is then analysed using Desmet and Pohlmeier's Framework for Positive Design. The data collection involved document analysis and in-depth interviews with key stakeholders. The interviews included tenants who were in arrears and participated in the program: housing staff; management; project officers and client services officers; staff from other organisations; trainers and project coordinators.

The Frame Creation process involves taking a step back from the 'reality' of the project and looking at the problem from a different perspective. The Frame Creation workshop was facilitated internally at the Designing Out Crime Centre by the researchers that conducted the evaluation. The alternative design emerging from this process will contribute to addressing arrears management from an alternative perspective using core values and positive design approaches. More prototyping, testing, and analysis will take place during 2014 before a new exploration becomes implementable. This paper reveals a bridge between the implementation of a program following existing processes, and the development of an alternative design

that sets up an alternate agenda to approach programs within the Framework for Positive Design.

THE SUSTAINABLE TENANCIES PROGRAM

This program was conceived and implemented during 2013. It aimed to reduce arrears in housing estates in the South Western Sydney District. The tenancy management team from Housing NSW in the area liaised with stakeholders, developed the project proposal, and managed the project throughout its implementation. The specific objectives of the program, as extracted from their program proposal, were:

- To reduce rental arrears of participating tenants
- To increase management practices and staff skills in relation to arrears portfolios
- To provide training to staff and tenants on financial management
- To develop and implement a mentoring program for tenants to expand the benefits of the training, and to support tenants in their financial management strategies

Training and capacity building were adopted as the vehicle to achieve long-term outcomes in sustaining tenancies, whilst at the same time improving management practices. The program consisted of two parts: a) the financial training, and b) the mentoring program. The financial training involved a six-session course delivered by a facilitator with expertise in finance (training and advice). The training was delivered to a mixed cohort of Housing NSW staff and tenants experiencing arrears. The mentoring program was designed for tenants who undertook the financial training and wanted to become mentors. The mentoring program was coordinated by a local NGO at the community level. Informal activities were initiated to support further sharing of information and learning about financial habits and management practices.

The content of the training program included themes such as: 1) Communication and conflict resolution; 2) Needs versus wants and emotional spending; 3) The basic budgeting model using the 'velcro' analogy; 4) Tips and tricks to spending with sense; 5) The advantages of saving money; 6) How your physical and mental health affect your financial health; 7) How to be self-sufficient now and in old age; and 8) Your money action plan, assumptions, challenges and support, targets and rewards. The trainer used presentations, interactive exercises, and handouts to deliver these contents.

The mentoring program involved more training on building personal confidence, communication, rapport, and interpersonal skills. The mentoring program used role play as an exercise to practice effective and positive communication between mentors and mentees. Handouts were also developed to support mentors during sessions, and a project officer was present whenever the mentors requested it.

Early assumptions in the conception of the program were that tenants experiencing arrears would be interested in

participating because it would benefit them personally (in learning personal finance management and gaining experience as mentors). This kind of training and mentoring experience it was assumed could lead to future employment opportunities.

The success factors stated in the program proposal were ambitious. Apart from reduction in rental arrears during peak times (e.g. Christmas), it was thought that tenants would be able to independently sustain their tenancies after the program. It was also felt that this program would provide the type of training that could increase the chances for paid employment for tenants, and that Housing NSW staff would translate the financial training into improved arrears management practices.

The program evaluation

The evaluation revealed insights on how participants experienced and reflected on this program. Overall, this program used training as a vehicle for change which is the traditional way in which Housing NSW operate. The novelty in this case was that they attempted to embed activities that elicited positive feelings and responses. For example sharing stories about living in public housing would elicit empathy between Housing staff and tenants. However, this program did not clearly communicate the empathy and trust agendas. It was expected that informal processes would flow naturally during and after program implementation. The following table shows a number of insights reported during the evaluation.

EVALUATION INSIGHTS (PARAPHRASED FROM INTERVIEWS) & FROM DOCUMENT ANALYSIS	ANALYSIS (USING DESMET AND POHLMAYER, 2013)
Conception	
<p>Incorporating the lessons from the finalized community development strategy to tenancy management practices was an underlying aspiration behind this program.</p> <p>The proposal had to be sent for approval quickly and there was no opportunity for refinement of the idea; any adaptation would have to happen during the implementation.</p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>(Housing NSW Manager)</i></p> <p>The proposal was written using a template with emphasis on management efficiency, which limited the flexibility in the scope in terms of social outcomes.</p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>(From document analysis)</i></p>	<p>Applying community development strategies to Housing NSW core business can be interpreted as conflicting. As a government agency it is expected that Housing NSW offers support to community groups to address issues such as financial stress. However as the landlord, Housing is in the position of overseeing tenants' timely payments. Teaching tenants about financial literacy appears to be a compromised effort when it comes from the landlord.</p> <p>The program aimed to pursue personal goals (Design for personal significance) and encourage being a morally good person (Design for virtue). However, the goal — pay rent — was imposed as a central theme. This contradiction inhibited possibilities to achieve those objectives.</p>
Financial training and mentoring program	
<p>The financial training pursued two agendas: to teach practical habits for a healthy approach to personal finances, and to create an environment that fostered empathy and trust in the landlord-tenant relationship.</p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>(Trainer)</i></p> <p>The mentoring program required greater effort than it was anticipated because tenants needed formal training to develop interpersonal communication and mentoring skills. It was uncertain if this was contemplated in the proposal.</p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>(NGO liaison)</i></p> <p>The mentoring program did not have the frequency and attendance envisioned. Invited tenants showed interest in the beginning but many withdrew overtime.</p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>(Trainer & NGO liaison)</i></p> <p>Housing needs perseverance and more creative ways to capture the attention of tenants by tapping into their interests.</p> <p style="text-align: right;"><i>(Housing NSW staff)</i></p>	<p>The training fulfilled the Framework for Positive Design in that participants experienced positive affect (design for pleasure). Attendees said they enjoyed the training; it was interesting, valuable, and pleasant due to the sharing of positive stories and the high energy of the trainer.</p> <p>The mentoring program targeted pursuing personal goals (design for personal significance) because they learnt skills that made them better at managing finances and helping others. These activities addressed design for virtue in that mentors felt they were doing a morally good task in helping their peers.</p> <p>Despite that training and mentoring addressed the three aspects of positive design to a point, tenant participation decreased significantly. This could be due to the focus on a management issue, such as arrears (possibly an unattractive angle for tenants) lacking the component of design for pleasure.</p>

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EVALUATION INSIGHTS (PARAPHRASED FROM INTERVIEWS) & FROM DOCUMENT ANALYSIS	ANALYSIS (USING DESMET AND POHLMAYER, 2013)
Informal support	
<p>The informal tenant support group was proposed in a rather rigid format. Attendance decreased to the point that nobody attended the fourth meeting.</p> <p style="text-align: right;">(Trainer & NGO liaison)</p> <p>Future programs need to allow greater flexibility and soft entry approaches to instil a sense of ownership of informal sessions among tenants.</p> <p style="text-align: right;">(NGO liaison)</p>	<p>The assumption that informal groups and activities could grow in a snowball effect was an ambitious proposition. The evaluation data showed people would only commit to informal groups if they had a genuine connection to the program beyond paying the rent. It appears that the Framework for Positive Design and/or a Frame Creation approach could offer potential to identify what is really valuable to tenants and the values that will keep them committed over time.</p>

Table 1. Sustainable Tenancies Program Analysis Table
Source: Data analysis sheets 2013.

EXPLORING ALTERNATIVE DESIGNS

The alternative design for the Sustainable Tenancies program was developed following the Frame Creation model for innovation. The reason for using this model was that in the evaluation we identified that the program attempted to develop a novel way to solve the problem of arrears, but was using traditional methods to achieve it. Therefore, we needed to reconsider the conception of the project to reveal the different perspectives surrounding the problem and find fruitful frames for future innovation.

Frame Creation involves the following steps: 1) Archaeology, which reviews the recent history of the problem and its formulation; 2) Paradox, identifying the ‘what makes this problem hard to solve’ question; 3) Context and Field, are the steps that analyse stakeholders and investigate ‘what is important to them’; 4) Themes, is a step revealing the common values

important to stakeholders by means of associations and reflection on core human values; 5) Frames and Futures are the steps that allow a creative leap; the themes become frames by unpacking the values and turning them into novel ways to look at the original problem. To do so, it is necessary to tap into emotional experiences and experiences of meaning personal and collective; and 6) Transformation and Integration are the final steps that investigate the changes and practices required for implementation and to identify opportunities for new approaches (Dorst, 2013).

The Archaeology was analysed in the context of the evaluation presented in the section above. The Paradox identified was that the power relationship between the landlord and the tenants is unequal by nature, and this limits possibilities for the development of relationships based on trust and empathy. Therefore, the program coming from the Housing authority could be taken by tenants as another obligation of the tenancy agreement rather than an opportunity to learn and change. In the

Figure 1. Frame Creation emerging themes

Context and Field we analysed a wider number of stakeholders beyond the participating parties and what was important to them. We identified that a common interest was to contribute to activities conducive to improving living skills for tenants in need. The idea of offering support services that function as a starting point towards independent living and personal growth of tenants was important to all. According to this analysis the highlighted themes were: Nurturing, Resilience, Drive, Commitment and Thriving.

In the Frames step, we unpacked the themes and revealed that they relate to the idea that by providing opportunities for personal growth in a way that encourages people to take control of their life and exercise their autonomy could lead to more independent and resilient individuals. Therefore, nurturing activities that encourage individuals to stay strong in difficult circumstances could lead to confident and self-reliant individuals that will not only survive but thrive.

The frames discussed were based on metaphors and personal experiences related to thriving. One of the frames discussed was ‘the growth of a plant’; the other emerging frame was a ‘road trip’.

The ‘growth of a plant’ frame

A plant needs the adequate environment and the basic nutrients (sunlight, rich soil, and certain temperature) to thrive; in difficult circumstances (for example in a storm) a plant can still survive, but possibly will not flourish; and if the circumstances become too extreme or permanent the plant would die. However, plants naturally have adaptation mechanisms for survival and some can thrive in harsh conditions (e.g. mushrooms grow in the dark). This metaphor could be fruitful when explored from the perspective of the adaptation mechanisms. If used in the context of public housing tenants, then a future program could focus not on the financial training per se (which is similar to the nurturing of a plant), but on the everyday tasks and strategies tenants use to address financial difficulties and financial stress, their own adaptation mechanisms. This frame leads us to explore questions such as: what do tenants do at Christmas in order to enjoy the holiday? What do tenants do when they have to go to the doctor and get medicines not covered by medical subsidies? The responses will provide cues for positive design initiatives because there is a lot to learn about adaptation mechanisms from people who have experienced high levels of disadvantage throughout their lives. To further explore this we would need to research further elements that would lead to design for human flourishing, and the Framework for Positive Design counts with the components to achieve it.

The ‘growth of a plant’ frame opens opportunities for the design of services that focus on adaptability and resilience. According to the Framework for Positive Design (Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013), designs that foster personal (and financial) resilience mainly fit into the design for personal significance. Furthermore, resilience and adaptability when pursued in a communal manner (with the family unit, and/or local commu-

nity) could address design for virtue because by helping each other achieve financial success one can experience a virtuous behaviour. Under this frame, design for pleasure could be addressed by further exploring the metaphor of how a plant gets nurtured. For instance by finding the aspects in the design of a new service that really captures participant’s imagination in the financial goal they aspire to (beyond paying arrears), or in the methods of service delivery that engage tenants in pleasurable ways (e.g. through games or using attractive interfaces such as smart phones), designers can achieve a nurturing and pleasurable service experience.

The ‘road trip’ frame

This frame was discussed because it relies on the autonomy of the individual. A road trip is a pleasurable experience that involves personal motivation, so that it is not an obligation or something imposed. This frame is fruitful because it involves a time-space dimension, which is relevant for the design of time-bounded programs. For the design of programs using the road trip frame as a metaphor can help in the development of proposals that are responsive to the environment and which acknowledge autonomy and self-determination of individuals or groups to achieve goals. Using metaphors as tools for service design, as opposed to rigid management models, could result in practical proposals with the appropriate scope for success.

In practical terms, a road trip requires planning, self-determination, and decision making; it involves a dialogue with the external environment, and a sense of control over circumstances, as well as challenges out of one’s control. Using Desmet and Pohlmeier’s (2013) Framework for Positive Design, on an individual level, a road trip taps into the domain of personal meaning, goals, and aspirations. In the sense that one wants to move ahead, and reach the destination, this idea fits into the design for the personal significance component of the framework. A road trip elicits enjoying the moment and experiencing a series of temporary pleasures. When used as a metaphor this frame allows us to explore the moments or experiences that are most precious to tenants and implement them in the design of a service that addresses the dimension of design for pleasure. For example, exploring designs of services that help people saving for a car, for a road trip, or saving for a mobile phone in order to connect with loved ones. Using these frameworks to develop creative approaches for future programs is a needed shift to positively transform housing services. Design for virtue can also be fostered in services related to personal finance and more sustainable life styles. In the road trip frame a person can exercise autonomy by taking his or her family on the road to financial success, take the driver’s seat and lead their loved ones to a better future, and in that way fulfil the design for virtue aspect of the framework. Designing services using the frames resulting from Frame Creation and the Framework for Positive Design could also contribute to a more pleasurable, virtuous, and fulfilling experience for the staff delivering services and for the housing authority as an organisation.

Figure 2. Emerging frames analyzed in the context of the Framework for Positive Design

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The final steps in the Frame Creation model, Futures, Transformation, and Integration are to be explored within the environment of the organisation(s) that manage complex problems. The Frame Creation exercise has opened up possibilities to explore financial management with public housing tenants more broadly (not limited to arrears management). The evaluation of the program illustrated that in its proposal stage the program was ambitious and relied on assumptions of good will; for instance, the assumption that tenants would be highly motivated to commit to the informal support group did not happen. Gauging individuals' motivations to commit to social programs is almost impossible when programs are developed from the top-down. The alternative frames presented are conducive to novel designs in which personal motivation can be further explored from a bottom up approach using human centred design. Desmet and Pohlmeier's (2013) Framework for Positive Design enriches the conception of a design brief because it adds a layer of depth to the proposed frames so that in the design of a service for the purposes of achieving sustainable tenancies, other deep components of positive design and human flourishing can be addressed.

A key lesson from this analysis is that in the context of housing and family services, applying design tools based on positive design is highly relevant. Addressing subjective well-being in public housing environments require approaches that see the existing features of public housing tenants in a positive light and as strengths. The use of the Frame Creation model and the Framework for Positive Design revealed different perspectives to address key issues from the program in more creative ways that have not been identified before. Bottom up approaches that are centred on tenants and understand their values, meanings, and emotions associated to their experience of

services could be the entry point to positive design leading to social innovation in public housing.

Finally, the proposed frames offer a new agenda that investigate on a deeper level what is meaningful to tenants, and indicates a way forward in how services could address subjective well-being. Looking to arrears management from a positive perspective leads us to a research agenda guided by questions such as: why do some public housing tenants fail to pay their rent? What are the adaptation mechanisms public housing tenants use to manage their household finances in a context of scarce resources? And, How can organisations apply appropriate and effective design tools to achieve human flourishing and subjective well-being? Using the Framework for Positive Design explicitly, as well as the Frame Creation process, could lead to the exploration of creative ways to address financial sustainability for tenants tapping into their personal interests, goals, and values.

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EMOTIONAL ADAPTATION TO CLIMATE CHANGE: KEY FOUNDATION FOR A NEW ECO-CENTERED PARADIGM

Santiago Aparicio Velásquez
Ministry of Information and Communication Technology
of Colombia
✉ saporicio00@gmail.com

Isabel Cavelier Adarve
Independent Association of Latin America and the
Caribbean - AILAC
✉ isabelcavelier@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The effects of climate change have ceased to be a mere prediction for the future. The intensification of extreme weather events, their abrupt consequences, and the increasing vulnerability to their harmful effects, has brought adaptation to climate change to the forefront of the public agenda. Traditionally, adaptation has been understood to include 'hard' infrastructure measures, and 'soft' actions. However, the challenges posed to our communities have demonstrated to go well beyond their psychological and emotional preparedness to cope with them. This article aims at highlighting the importance of emotional adaptation to the effects of climate change as a tool for comprehending the changes that are occurring, cope with them, and then build a new kind of relationship with the environment. The article argues that emotional adaptation, fostered through art and cultural identity strengthening, is a useful means for achieving long-term sustainability by appealing to a profound and structural behavioural transformation.

KEYWORDS: *climate change, adaptation, emotional adaptation, cultural agency, art, symbolism, cultural identity*

INTRODUCTION

The traditional definition of adaptation to climate change has its merits and limitations. The IPCC has defined adaptation as the '[a]djustment in natural or human systems to a new or changing environment. (...) [It] refers to adjustment in natural or human systems in response to actual or expected climatic stimuli or their effects, which moderates harm or exploits beneficial opportunities' (IPCC, 2001). According to the World Bank (2013), "'Hard' adaptation measures usually imply the use of specific technologies and actions involving capital goods, such as dikes, seawalls and reinforced buildings, whereas 'soft' adaptation measures focus on information, capacity building, policy and strategy development, and institutional arrangements'. When analyzed against a broad understanding of the Earth's systems as being interconnected in a complex web of relationships, where the human societies are part of a wider, unified system, the traditional definition of adaptation falls short in understanding the range of actions that are needed to cope with climate change.

In fact, those usually called 'hard' or 'soft' adaptation actions can be better understood as being part of a wide spectrum,

which includes both the human and the non-human lead actions aimed at coping with the effects to climate change, from variations in the structure (and infrastructure) of the systems, and changes in behavioral patterns.

Mind-shifts are fundamental to be able to cope with the impact of climate change. The purpose of this text is to put forward the concept of *emotional adaptation* to climate change as part of these sorts of actions. Departing from a concrete experience carried on at 'Las Delicias' water stream in Bogotá, Colombia, we have attempted to better understand processes where a community changes its behavioural patterns, as well as its emotional relationship with the surrounding ecosystem.

For this purpose, this paper starts by defining the concept of emotional adaptation (section one); it then addresses the case study of 'Las Delicias' in order to see how emotional adaptation was reflected in this community-based project (section two), and finishes with some concluding remarks on the utility of this concept for communities and their relationship to the environment (section three).

EMOTIONAL ADAPTATION AND THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE COMMUNITY AND THE ECOSYSTEM

A crucial factor for achieving long-term sustainability is developing emotional adaptation strategies that appeal to a profound and structural behavioural transformation. Our proposal of emotional adaptation emphasizes the experiential and imaginative level in the community-based work, thus building robust cultural changes that create a sustainable relationship with the surrounding ecosystem.

Emotional adaptation to climate change is defined here as the transformational process of achieving the awareness of the climate change phenomenon that is visibly occurring, comprehending, and experiencing psychological and emotional preparedness to these radical changes, and gaining a new perception of the relationship of humans to their environment, while considering one's self as an organic part of the ecosystem. Emotional adaptation is fundamental to understanding the effects of climate change, building the resilience to cope with it, and then building a new kind of relationship with the environment where communities see themselves as players of a broader system where close and harmonic interaction with the overall system itself is necessary for survival and well being.

The territories, landscapes, and climate system (atmosphere, hydrosphere, biosphere, and geosphere, and their interactions) are crucial for human survival and subsistence, but are also vital because they are the frameworks in which cultural identity is anchored. The changes that occur to the climate system affect the landscape and socio-economic scheme and as a consequence the cultural realm of the communities is deeply impacted.¹ In this context a deep understanding and interpretation of what is happening is required to cope with the changes and anchor the cultural identity of the community to the reality of a changing place with a sense of belonging.

In Larry Robinson's words, '[a]s human beings we have a need for place – where we can be connected to a community of people, plants, animals and the land. Without this, we feel lost, alone and alienated. The world also needs us to belong to it since it is only when we inhabit a place that we care for it and assume responsibility for it. If we regard the world as only a place we are visiting, we have little interest in protecting it' (Burzell & Chalquist, 2009, p.29).

Cultural identity plays a key role as it directly contributes to the construction of our reality. We need to feel part of the context in which our livelihood is embedded as a previous step to protecting an ecosystem with a sense of ownership and belonging. In this context, the creation and appropriation

of narratives about the surrounding reality is fundamental. 'Stories can inflame the imagination. Stories about our families and ancestors, stories about trees and animals and rocks around us, stories about the stars and planets and gods can help find and remember our place and anchor us in time and space. In re-storying the world, we can restore it' (Burzell & Chalquist, 2009, p.29).

A crucial element of the cultural identity, as one of the routes for emotional adaptation, is the ritualism and mysticism that surrounds each culture, which is the spinal cord for the cosmogony of people's lives. It permits having a mindset that facilitates acquiring an understanding of the world and the person's place in it. The existence of a strong cultural identity that includes a particular ritualism and mysticism can be understood as a fundamental tool to achieve emotional adaptation to climate change. The relevance of symbols and myths has been highlighted by Mircea (1991, p.62) when he explains that '[t]o transcend profane time and re-enter into mythical great time is equivalent to a revelation of ultimate reality that is strictly metaphysical, and can be approached in no other way through myths and symbols'. Emotional adaptation is at the crossroads between the need to gain physical contact with nature that can contribute to recovering an inner ritualistic practice, and the creation of stronger relationships with the environment that foster the adoption adaptive practices involving the community and the ecosystem.

As this inner process occurs, an intuitive understanding is triggered that makes us realize that affecting nature is equivalent to affecting one's self. Through that process, a broader transformation detonates. This is why structural behavioural changes can only be achieved if they come from within each person and from within the community rather than through indoctrination processes where 'green' actions are made in automated and repetitive ways without a reflexive process behind them. Part of the strength of *emotional adaptation* processes is the recognition that the climate change effects we are experiencing are part of a bigger complex system. In this system, humans are agents capable of finding solutions, and are an integral part of the system that is being threatened by climate change.

In this context, art has a crucial role as an emotional medium and creator of symbolism. Art as a bridge, a new language that establishes deep communication between nature and the individuals, is a vehicle to generate a sense of belonging and environmental awareness to guarantee sustainability and recovery of ecosystems. As the artist David Buckland states: 'There is a need to shift our mental and physical state from observation to habitation. This is artistic territory; it is what artists do – they uncover the hidden, the unpalatable, the unstated, whether it be in love, ethics or values (...)' (Buckland & Wainwright, 2010, p.8). During the case study conducted as part of our research, collaborative community art installations functioned as a bridge that encouraged community 'dialogue' with the ecosystem understood as a *living being*.

1 In its Fifth Assessment Report (AR5) the IPCC re-confirmed that climate change has affected many physical and biological systems (IPCC 2014). Based on its observations, it concluded that 'changes in climate have caused impacts on natural and human systems on all continents and across the oceans. Evidence of climate-change impacts is strongest and most comprehensive for natural systems'.

The experience carried out at 'Las Delicias' water stream allowed us to better understand processes where a community changes its behavioural patterns and emotional relationship with its surrounding ecosystem, and to observe how this served as an adaptation tool that fostered further adaptation actions carried forward with the ecosystem. The following section focuses on this case study.

EMOTIONAL ADAPTATION AT 'LAS DELICIAS' WATER STREAM

Edward O. Wilson, a Harvard University scientist and Pulitzer Prize-winning author, defines biophilia as 'the urge to filiate with other forms of life. (...) He and his colleagues argue that humans have an innate affinity for the natural world, probably a biologically based need integral to our development as individuals. In short, we need experiences in nature more than we know' (Burzell & Chalquist, 2009, page no.207). In the same line of thought, the renamed eco-therapist Richard Louv, has explored how one of the reasons that we are experiencing a great disconnect with nature is the growing gap between culture and nature on the psyches of humans, especially children, and coins the term 'nature deficit disorder', which can be overcome through the deep experience and contact with nature (Louv, 2008).

Our research has focused on the space for bridging that gap, as a strategy for emotional adaptation to climate change. For this reason, the case study conducted at 'Las Delicias' stream focused on the use of 'cultural agency'² through art as a means to increase the sense of belonging of the community to the ecosystem, and to foster the start of a behavioral change to transform its engagement with its surrounding habitat. Through this exercise we were able to see how individuals adopted greener and more harmonic attitudes aimed at the conservation of their neighboring ecosystem.

The initial artistic intervention that inspired this research was carried out in September 2011.³ With the support of the Bogotá city administration, in particular the environment district office, and Conservation International, an artistic intervention that was carried out in the context of a project to recover the 'Las Delicias' water stream. Its purpose was to increase the level of awareness and ownership in the surrounding community, using art as a means to do it. In this context, the project gathered a group of artists from the community itself, as well as a broader group of artists from Bogotá interested in environmental issues.

The community's testimonies were recorded, and along with the media coverage and the high level of engagement of col-

laborators of different disciplines and industries, the case study demonstrated how various kinds of artistic languages were successful at encouraging the community to communicate with their neighboring ecosystem and re-build a deep relationship with it. More than 200 people from the community of 'Bosque Calderon', 'Castillo', and 'Chapinero Alto' neighbourhoods, the three surrounding neighborhoods of 'Las Delicias' stream, were engaged during the process.

The testimonies demonstrate the process of behavioural change that took place under an emotional adaptation process. A good example of this is Benedicto Galindo's words, a community member and leader living near the stream, who expressed how moved he was by his daughter's sudden interest in the stream after years of apathy:

For sure today important impacts occurred. My daughter, who is a physician, has never been interested in the stream, neither walking over the bank nor helping me in taking care of it, and today she was really present. Last night when I was writing the poem I recited today, she got near me and asked me what I was doing. I explained it to her, and she asked me if she could recite the poem on the 'stage' for me. To me, seeing her today walking over the stream's bank after all these years of complete apathy moves me a lot. Outcomes will become more tangible in long-term, but be sure that there will be important outcomes.⁴

Testimonies of the members of the collective of artists that participated in the project also reconfirm how the artistic experience worked as a powerful transformational tool. The following are some examples of the artistic interventions that were carried out as part of the project.

Example One: Three Musicians, Mariposa Solar, Pedro Crump, and Héctor Buitrago, created music dedicated to the positive vibrations the water was making over the environment.

Hector Buitrago, a musician from "CONECTOR Cantoalagua de Aterciopelados", stated that

Figure 1. Hector Buitrago honouring water through singing. Photo By: Alejandra Ariza (2011)

2 We use the term 'cultural agency' in the sense described by Doris Sommer (Sommer, 2006) which relates to 'a variety of public practices that link creativity with social contributions'.
3 A complete account of the project from September 2011 can be found at <http://artasabridge.wordpress.com/case-study/>.

4 All testimonies have been translated from Spanish to English by the authors, procuring to keep translations as literal as possible.

The art for awakening the hearts of people that are living nearby the ecosystems and that maybe do not have that awareness, is the most powerful tool for opening those hearts and the consciences so that we can again reconnect with the ancestral spirits that live in these places.

Pedro Crump, another musician participating, expressed:

One way of creating awareness is saying things, but through art and the human expression is (...) maybe stronger, it reaches more people to their hearts.

Example Two: Ecological Murals: Urban Collective Art (Doble C y WAP) and Gladys Ortiz, using environmentally safe aerosol paint and environmentally safe paint respectively, composed two large-scale murals.

The artists testified to the impact of their intervention. Danilo Ochoa, illustrator and graffiti artist from the 'Artes Urbanas' crew, and an inhabitant neighborhood Bosque Calderón, stated:

From art you can sensitize, you can make an appropriation of spaces, appropriation of territories, one part of appropriation is making you feel the owner of this [nature] without being the unique owner but with a responsibility for taking care of it.

Figure 5.1 Neighborhood Children artists, Alfonso Ariza (Artist) and Santiago Aparicio V (Creative Director)

Figure 2. Mural in Process

Figure 3. Final Mural Photos By: Alejandra Ariza (2011)

Figure 4. Graffiti artist – WAP. Photo By: Alejandra Ariza (2011)

Example Three: The renowned Colombian artist, Alfonso Ariza, inspired by the drawings of 40 neighborhood children on the river above, created a mosaic 60 square meters wide by the bank of the creek.

In Ariza's words:

Raising the awareness of the preservation of resources is creating awareness of the wildlife that exists, the flora that exist in every region and also raising awareness of the esthetical part, of how you can do something esthetical with recycled materials.

Figure 5.2 Mosaic detail. Photos By: Alejandra Ariza (2011)

Figure 6. Community member cropping native tree over the riverside. Photo By: Alejandra Ariza (2011)

Figure 7. Recycle tree under construction process. Photo By: Alejandra Ariza (2011)

Figure 8. Minimal Gallery Exhibition. Photo by: Santiago Aparicio V.

Example Four: Community Reforestation: The community planted 300 native trees over the bank of the creek, each one was given a God mother or God father committed to taking care of them.

Example Five: Recycle Trees⁵: The artist, Reynaldo Tibaduiza created structures with recycled material picked that day by the community from the stream and turned them into trees with the aim of creating symbolic significance that give dimension to this problem.

This first artistic intervention of 2011 created a significant inertia that provoked a ripple effect. The experience has been followed by a series of artistic interventions that have been activating the ecosystem (territory-neighboring community), and have contributed to positioning the stream as the most visited ecological public park of the city. It truly empowered the community to replicate similar artistic interventions that created a virtuous circle.

One of the initial tangible effects was the significant reduction of quantity of tons of contaminating waste that the neighboring community was throwing into the stream. This has benefited the ecosystem's functioning, which in turn has a positive impact over all the population living downstream.

Later on, from February 16th to March 3rd, 2012, at Minimal-Arte, a local art gallery near 'Las Delicias' stream, an exhibition called 'Dialogues with Las Delicias Stream' was put up with all the artefacts that represented the creation of environmental awareness of 'Las Delicias' stream. The purpose of the exhibition was to engage other people of the neighborhoods that surrounded the stream to visit and promote the occurrence of future community artistic interventions, and further increase the environmental awareness among the population. The gallery exhibited the community children's drawings of the stream, the phrases they expressed to the Stream, a photo-slideshow, the recycled-material tree sculptures, and a trailer video-clip that documented the whole experience.

5 The artifacts that give dimension to the findings of this case study were also presented at the Lethaby Gallery in London on the 8th December 2011, as part of the 'MA Applied Imagination' research project that Santiago Aparicio V presented at Central Saint Martins School of Art and Design, University of the Arts London.

With the support of Conservation International, an additional campaign was conducted to invite crucial stakeholders from private and public sectors (environmental authorities) to the gallery in order to receive their feedback and engagement. This opened new doors for these kinds of interventions in Colombia and was a crucial step to promoting the process of replication of this experience through art techniques used at 'Las Delicias' stream.

Further on, on the 5th of May, 2012, the community leaders that have been empowered as eco-touristic guides (with the support of Conservation International), and organized the 'Carnavalito del Agua' (Little Water Carnival) where, through artistic and cultural activities, they engaged the local community to gain awareness on the valuable water stream that they have in their own neighborhood.

On the 27th of October, 2012, the local mayor of the area, the local community councils and other institutions (such as the environmental police), united to create a space that invited cultural collectives to an event called 'La Toma del Agua en la Quebrada' (drinking water from the stream) that promoted the conservation of the ecosystem. Art was again at the core of the planned activities and once again culture was used as a means to raise awareness.

During November 2012, the two institutions 'Sociedad Invisible Artistic Collective' and 'The Agency' united to design a project that reactivates 'Las Delicias' Stream's surroundings to a place 'full of colors'. For this purpose a festival was organized. On that day, more than 300 people enjoyed street food, performances, music, and face painting, and participated in a major photo shooting activity called 'The river of Colors' ('Río de Colores').

Then during the last quarter of 2013, a performance called 'Agua Quebrada' was executed, where the Foundation Naturaleza y Patrimonio, awarded with the Art and Nature Scholarship of the Distrital Institute of Arts — IDARTES 2013, made an artistic proposal that made visible the crystalline water surging from the east mountains and polluted during its path to the river mouth. Although the reach of this particular project was not restricted to 'Las Delicias' stream, it is worth mentioning its impact in all the east mountains of Bogotá, where 'Las Delicias' stream originates, along with other neighboring streams such as 'La Vieja'. It is worth highlighting the follow-

Figure 9. “Río de Colores” performance. Photo By: Oscar Filigrana

Figure 10. Stream’s silhouette/course painting over Bogotá’s financial street, 72nd street. Photo by: Carolina Cruz

ing components of this project: a ‘Sensory capsule’ of the East Mountains and ‘La Vieja’ stream, healing and reflection concerts, and hikes to the east mountains. This project had an artistic intervention in the street, where images of the forest reserve of the east mountains flora and fauna were presented, in addition to the interpretation of the riverbed of the stream ‘La Vieja’ through the road and sidewalks of the 72nd street.

One year after the artistic intervention occurred on September 2011, the following testimonies of crucial players in the community system demonstrated the structural changes that had been fostered through this process:

Sofia López, Comm-unitary Eco-touristic Guide:

A web has been threaded, a big goal was threading a strong environmental web. This facilitates communitarian strengthening. Some of the people that live near the stream keep being just neighbors not the stream, the ecosystem (...). People from around all the city are coming, the universities are engaged in the process, the NGOs, the public institutions, the schools... young people have been near the process when we gave them the possibility of being truly themselves [facilitating artistic and cultural spaces for them]. Through the community kitchen we have found possibilities of anchoring and reaching the community. At the beginning when I began climbing it [the mountain that hosts Las Delicias Stream] it was boring...I accepted the job as eco-touristic guide that International Conservation (CI) offered me because I needed the money...but now I have seen the splendour of the place...we miss valuable things in everyday life. I have learnt to admire myself through my work’s mission. The process of restoration of the stream is the creation and un-covering of the identity of the place. (...) Changing behaviours is a long term task. (...) Bringing the kids to the stream again and developing artistic, cultural, ludic activities with them was crucial for achieving this whole change; they became sensitized and began taking stories to their parents. The neighboring adults then have really got engaged in the process and you can see them on the stream, it is all thanks to the children.

Patricia Bejarano, Coordinator of the Conservation International project:

The two things that created the change were: 1) Having the right communication strategy, and the right medium to engage the community (through art and culture), giving a place to each. 2) Really contributing to create a web, you meet me by chance, then you introduce me to others, others introduce themselves to others and so on, friendships have been created. Even a couple fell in love walking up the stream and mountains and now they are married. Academics, students, priests, public institutions are now engaged. The big achievement is that the inertia is now rolling on, and it does not need Conservation International as an indispensable engine anymore, it’s now moving by itself.

Diana Aya, young community leader, who worked at Conservation International and is also an inhabitant of the ‘Moraci’ stream, nearby to ‘Las Delicias’:

The process developed around the streams from artistic expressions, has positioned as a necessary amalgam to join the technic and scientific restoration actions of the streams with the community dynamics. This by integrating diversity and making visible aspects that make more beautiful and makes them notorious and visible at specific moments, calling people to embrace natural spaces, giving time so that life’s cycles can make their purpose, while time passes and a tree grows and birds fly, people embrace the streams and re-learn to understand them as a fundamental part of their environment, and therefore from their life. They turn in encounter spaces for enjoying, living together and for making conservation.

Andrés Plazas, Walker and Leader of the NGO ‘Amigos de la Montaña’:

In Las Delicias stream restoration process it has become evident that the problems associated with apparently dissimilar issues like environment, safety and community strengthening, that traditionally will be afforded through different disciplines (biology, safety experts-policemen and scientists), is really the same one thing. It’s the enjoyment of the territory and its care, with the marvelous pretext of the encounter around art and culture that creates the weaving of social fabric. The green threads in the community a need for maturation/maturing, for its well being, with a strengthening of the identity and confidence that the same community is the one that can create the solutions to their own problems.

Octavio Rodriguez, a sociologist that works at Conservation International and has been the supporter of the community strategy over the restoration process of Las Delicias stream:

The impact of the artistic interventions and the culture of environmental awareness are evident in the quantity of positive comments that have arrived to CI signaling the importance of this project. This is also reflected in the lyrics of the hip-hop music of the community groups and artworks of the artists. [There has been] relevant coverage of mass media and alternative media of the cultural interventions, in addition to the incorporation of new social agents. Nowadays other institutions keep summing up to Las Delicias’ initiative, such as Los Andes University, the Distrital University, SENA, Mesa Interlocal Río Salitre, and Veeduría Ciudadana de Bogotá.

As a consequence of these experiences, people are now actively discussing and arguing around the stream, which demonstrates the relevance that the ecosystem by itself is acquiring and its increased liveliness. This case study constituted a

new form of knowledge, not just because it raised the environmental awareness of the inhabitants of neighborhoods surrounding 'Las Delicias', but especially because it uncovered the key role that art, as a tool for creating emotional adaptation to climate change, may play in fostering this awareness. By involving people's emotions, this form of communication is likely to be more effective and long lasting than traditional environmental education, prohibitions, or restoration efforts.

Recognizing the value of their ecosystem, the value of the pure water that the 'Las Delicias' stream carries just beside their neighborhoods, how the water comes from the pristine higher mountains, and how it's a privilege having it, and consequently embracing the stream to take care of it, is the new way to connect to their territory. Seeing the extreme variability of water level that has existed in other places of the city helps them recognize the risk of experiencing similar phenomena. By reducing the level of waste thrown into the stream and by collaborating to recover native vegetation along the stream's bank, this process has achieved ecosystem recovery and increased resilience, thanks to the emotional preparedness and awareness of the radical changes that are occurring with climate variability. The agents have reduced their vulnerability while acquiring a new perception on the relation between the environment and the community.

In this example emotional adaptation, fostered through art and cultural identity strengthening, became a development tool that promoted conservation, ecosystem recovery, and at the same time increased the level of comprehension of the threat of climate change on the rational and imaginative levels. This comprehension is part of a real structural transformation, where the complex problems the community is facing are approached by other disciplines, giving place to deep social and environmental impacts. Shifting the egocentric paradigm that predominantly rules to an eco-centered paradigm has fostered the key foundations that are promoting the behavioral change that will hopefully lead to a more sustainable future.

EMOTIONAL ADAPTATION: A USEFUL CONCEPT FOR COMMUNITIES AND THE ENVIRONMENT

In the process of conducting this research, we have identified two possible ways to foster emotional adaptation: a) using 'cultural agency', where art and its symbols impact emotions and therefore serve as a medium; and b) strengthening local cultural identity with relation to the environment. These two alternatives are not mutually exclusive, and should both be accompanied by the promotion of direct physical contact and intimacy with nature, while acknowledging the power of nature to create a transformational process, which aids emotional and psychological healing to life's stressful events.

In the first case (using cultural agency) art has played a crucial role as a medium through which the psychological shift required for emotional adaptation was fostered. During the case study developed at 'Las Delicias' stream during Septem-

ber 2011 the collaborative community art installations functioned as a symbolic bridge between the community and the surrounding ecosystem. This 'dialogue' inspired a new understanding of the ecosystem as a living being. In that particular context, art, a new language connecting nature and the individuals, generated a new sense of belonging and environmental awareness about sustainability and the recovery of ecosystems.

Strengthening local cultural identity with relation to the environment (the second method identified) was at the same time a consequence of the enhanced cultural agency through art, and a means to multiply and erase inertia around a broader transformation rooted in a profound mind-shift in the community actors. The local actors' engagement with the artistic interventions was instrumental in re-creating a new local sense of identity. This was rooted in a new understanding of the role that the stream plays in their day-to-day lives, and the role that they, as agents of transformation, play with in the recovery and conservation of the stream.

Once communities recover and recognize through such a process of emotional adaptation that they play an active role in the systemic functioning of ecosystems and nature as a whole, they become more reflexive and conscious of their everyday actions and their impact over the system.

People are used to underestimating the value and beauty of those things that appear to be common to their everyday lives, taking them for granted. Nature and its components are not an exception to this, hence they become an additional element of the landscape that we tend to ignore. This contributes to deepening a disconnection between the community and the environment. Emotional adaptation processes can help to give a new meaning to the space where life takes place, placing the ecosystem and its elements at the core, with human communities as an integral part of a much broader system.

The case study showed the close relationship that exists between emotional adaptation and sustainability. The process of behavioral change that was fostered worked as an effective way to increase the awareness and understanding of climate change. It had direct impacts in the increased resilience of the community and the ecosystem. One of the most difficult issues over the behavioural change regarding environmental issues is that the environment is a collective asset where impacts are usually intangible, and where a perfect assignation of costs is virtually impossible. If people do not comprehend the complexity of the system, then themselves and their descendants will be directly affected.

Emotional adaptation poses as a suitable concept to develop and apply over public policy frameworks, as contributing to the creation of structural changes. These in turn can contribute to the establishment of a stronger relationship with the environment, which individuals feel an integral part of. This process of new understanding makes us realize that affecting the environment is equivalent to affecting one's self, and a process of transformation detonates. Structural behavioral changes must come from within, and should not be achieved

through indoctrination processes where green actions are acted without a reflexive process behind them. The community from the experiential and imaginative level is the one that can construct cultural changes that create a sustainable relation with the ecosystem.

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Santiago Aparicio is a social entrepreneur and 'Government and International Relations' professional, with particular emphasis in innovation, management, and sustainability issues. He has worked within the corporate, advocacy and policy levels in various projects in Colombia. On December 2011, he finished an MA in 'Applied Imagination' at Central Saint Martins College of Art and Design, University of the Arts London. Since then he has been working in the Colombian public sector encouraging social innovation as a development tool to tackle development challenges. Currently he works at the Ministry of Information and Communication Technology as Subdirector of Processes of Adoption, and is professor of Social Innovation at the Master in Development Practice (MDP) of Universidad de los Andes.

Isabel Cavalier Adarve is a lawyer and socio-cultural studies professional, and holds an LLM in International Law from Cambridge University, UK. She has published various books and articles related to human rights and climate change issues. She worked for several years as an internal advisor in economic, social and environmental issues at the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Colombia where she was lead negotiator on climate finance and advised the Ministry on the Colombian proposals for the definition of the post 2015 sustainable development agenda. She currently leads the team that supports the Independent Association of Latin America and the Caribbean (AILAC) in the UNFCCC negotiations.

The authors write in their personal capacity.

BIOPHILIC DESIGN, RESTORATIVE ENVIRONMENTS AND WELL-BEING

Ana Karinna Hidalgo

PhD student, Faculty of Environmental Design, University of Calgary

✉ akhidalg@ucalgary.ca

ABSTRACT

Well-being in cities can be addressed from the perspective of multiple disciplines. Urban design can contribute to creating built environments within nature with tangible elements to provide psychological restoration that releases stress and mental fatigue. To do so, many design approaches, such as biophilic design, biomimicry, and eco-cities can make a contribution to this topic. This paper is focused on biophilic design as an urban design approach aimed at understanding connections between natural and built environments in relation to psychological restoration. Important inputs from environmental psychology and public health are also considered to understand people's responses to different natural and built environments. This paper consists of an extensive literature review of these disciplines and approaches in order to provide designers with elements to be considered for the design of restorative environments. These elements may include natural water features, natural light and colors, vegetation, and well-designed buildings to improve people's well-being.

KEYWORDS: *well-being, psychological restoration, biophilic design, environmental psychology, restorative environments*

INTRODUCTION

Biophilic environments in urban spaces can provide people with psychological restorative experiences by releasing mental fatigue and decreasing their levels of stress. This restoration process in turn improves people's well-being. Public urban spaces should be considered as restorative places where more people could benefit from biophilic elements.

Urban spaces are constantly changing over time. The uses of urban spaces depend not only on their function but also on the historical, cultural, social, and economic aspects of a city. Nowadays, urban researchers are focusing on the social and cultural aspects of cities and the interconnections of people within urban places (Gehl, 2010; Madanipour, 2010). However, this is not the only direction that urban theories are taking. For instance, UN-Habitat (2013a) is challenging city leaders to design good cities and to consider the streets as public spaces and drivers of well-being where all users can be engaged in different ways (UN-Habitat, 2013b).

Well-being has been studied from different perspectives. Urban design historically relates the concept of well-being to comfort status that people obtain in public places. This does not imply that this objective was always achieved, but that this field is in the search for promoting well-being and the understanding of the urban components of it. Most of the theories

related to well-being in public spaces refer to the way people understand, experience, and perceive a space because of its legibility (Lynch, 1960; Appleyard, 1976), or the way people enjoy outdoor activities (Jacobs, 1961; Madanipour, 2010; Gehl, 2011).

How people experience the environment and how they are related to it is twofold. On one hand, the built environment is a result of its physical characteristics, whereas, on the other, the quality of the urban space, as a result of the wealth, culture, social issues, and age of the city, also takes part in people's perceptions (Steg et al, 2013). All these variables identify a city and influence its residents, who in turn are able to change the environment both positively and negatively. The environment influences each individual differently; what is common ground is the set of elements suggested by environmental psychology based on experiments and evidence from this field.

Kopec (2006), Gifford (2007) and Steg et al. (2013) offer a wide range of evidence from several research studies on natural and built environments. From these results, and in order to promote people's well-being, environmental psychologists suggest the use of natural features within urban spaces that can provide positive outcomes at different stages and for different purposes, such as forest-like playgrounds, green roofs, edible gardens, and tree lined boulevards. These features are developed by approaches different from urban design theory,

for instance, ecological cities (Register, 2010), biomimicry (Benyus, 2002), and biophilic design (Wilson, 1984; Kellert et al., 2008).

One of the main benefits of nature is the psychological restorative effect that will be addressed in this paper. Firstly, this paper presents the definition of well-being and restoration as outcomes to be achieved by design, and the definition of stress in order to understand one of the factors that is threatening people's well-being. Secondly, the concept of biophilia and biophilic urban design spaces will be provided. This section presents the state of the art of this approach based on the work by prominent researchers in the field. The third section addresses the relationship between psychological restoration and biophilic design, and discusses the positive outcomes from natural environments based on relevant evidence. Finally, some suggestions about further research are proposed, as well as the need of an interdisciplinary approach to offer more appropriate responses to urban stressors.

WELL-BEING, STRESS AND RESTORATION

For the purpose of this paper, it is important to define some interdisciplinary keywords in order to maintain a common language. Well-being, stress and restoration will be considered from a psychological perspective with insights from public health, which will be later understood in the context of the urban design field.

The pursuit of well-being is a goal for people around the world. The lack of well-being is an impediment not only for individual development but also for the development of an equal society. One of the factors that negatively impacts well-being is stress. For the purpose of this paper, and based on the definitions from other fields, well-being is understood as the condition of being healthy from a psychological perspective (NWIA, 2011), and having social interactions of good quality (HRSDC, 2013). Subjective well-being (SWB), widely employed in psychology and economics, refers to people's mood and emotions that result from being exposed to events or stimuli of different nature (Diener, 2000). Subjective well-being is defined as good mental states that include positive and negative self evaluations reported by people about their lives and the affective reactions to their experiences (OECD, 2013).

Cities aim to provide people with environments that improve their quality of life. However, cities, and specifically streets, produce urban stressors that threaten the ability of people to restore themselves from stress and mental fatigue (Kopeck, 2006; Gifford, 2007). In this context, stress is a state of mental or emotional chaos that results from adverse or challenging circumstances that affects people's mental and even physical health. Psychological stress occurs when a person's perception of the environment is above or below her capacity of adaptation, which challenges or threatens well-being (Ulrich, 1986; Cohen et al., 2007). Psychological restoration is, in general, the ability of a person to overcome stress and mental fatigue, and experience mental rejuvenation.

Stress establishes links to health by affecting the immune system and provoking psychological problems (Bilotta & Evans, 2013). The ability to balance all aspects of life such as social, physical, spiritual, economic, and mental domains, can reduce the level of stress (CMHA). From an environmental perspective, stress is a human response to the imbalance between environment demands and the capability of human response (Steg et al., 2013). A continuous exposure to stress may influence and also affect physical health because of the biological processes or behavioral patterns that influence disease risk. Stress is a process where the person responds psychologically, physiologically and even behaviorally to a specific situation that challenges or threatens well-being (Ulrich, 1986).

From a psychological perspective, a person can be restored from stress by being exposed to nature. Restoration (from Latin *recreation*, *recreationis* = restoration, refreshment, and recovery), refers to the experience of both psychological and physiological recovery that is activated in specific environments (Joye & van den Berg, 2013). The capacity of people to recover their health status from illness or stress in urban environments is related to a successful achievement of well-being and the main concern of urban design.

Virtual and direct relation to nature and other features such as water, music, and colorful surfaces can be beneficial for psychological and physical health because of the reduction of the stress they promote. Robert Ulrich (1984; 1986) shows, for example, that even if healthcare facilities are stressful by themselves, patients and visitors get benefits from the presence of vegetation and green landscapes. He finds that patients recover more rapidly from a surgery if the window of their healing rooms shows green landscape compared to those that have a wall instead. His findings are acknowledged and used as a basis for stress restoration theories (Kopeck, 2006; Gifford, 2007; Joye & van der Berg, 2013).

Psychologists define two main theories about restorative environments that, despite focusing on different aspects of restoration, are related to each other because restoration is a multi-faceted process (Roe & Aspinall, 2011; Gifford, 2007; Kopeck, 2006). Therefore both theories, attention restoration theory (ART), and stress recovery theory (SRT), are considered here in order to have inputs for the development of a theoretical framework from an environmental perspective.

The ART focuses on the fatigue provoked by the active attention that people need during most of a workday. According to Rachel Kaplan & Steven Kaplan (1989), people need to go through four phases to overcome mental fatigue: fascination, directed attention to the fascinating environment, contemplation, and deeper restoration experience. Ulrich et al. (1991) propose the SRT by focusing on stress reduction from an affective and aesthetic response to the environment. People's preferences for natural landscapes, shown by their choices about where they live and recover, constitute the scientific evidence for this theory (Ulrich et al., 1991). SRT considers that restoration from stress occurs when it positively impacts people's well-being (Joye & van den Berg, 2013).

Restoration and well-being are concepts related to each other. From an urban design perspective, restorative spaces are ideal to provide people with stress recovery and mental fatigue release. Specific urban places such as parks, museums, spiritual temples, and healing buildings usually provide restorative experiences. Most of the elements that constitute these spaces include nature and the possibility to personalize the environment.

BIOPHILIA AND DESIGN

Edward O. Wilson, a well-known biologist, coined the term biophilia in his book *Biophilia* (1984). He defines biophilia as the innate urge of humans to affiliate with nature and other forms of life and life-like processes. The desire of having more livable habitats obeys this urge and is called aesthetic criteria (Wilson, 1984). Biophilia, ‘the innately emotional affiliation of human beings to other living organisms’ (Wilson, 1993, p. 31), is an integral part of the human development process and of the physical and mental growth. As a consequence individuals look for opportunities to enjoy nature outside cities because these are places that are usually not offering this type of refuges, such as tropical forests, the savannah of human ancestors (Heerwagen & Orians, 1993).

Even if biophilia has its origin in biological science, Wilson (2008) is aware that this term unites disciplines as a cause-and-effect explanation, for instance among biology, social sciences, and design. The inclusion of social aspects can be grounded on biophilia complexity by considering also cultural and ethnic differences among individuals and communities (Soulé, 1993).

Historically the built environment has been integrated with the natural environment, and traditionally local materials and processes constitute the local aesthetics and heritage of society. Nowadays, neither local materials nor local vegetation that protects endemic flora and fauna, which is vital to the biophilic approach, are used as they were before. Kellert et al. (2008) argue that biophilic design takes advantage of an intrinsic human affinity to incorporate natural and local systems and processes into the design of the built environment. People have given different values to nature according to its functions, for instance physical sustenance, experience and curiosity of people in contact with nature, the understanding of its systems and structures, communication and expression, mimicking its mechanics, and spiritual reverence and affiliation ties (Kellert & Wilson, 1993; Kellert, 2008).

Different biological perspectives of design have been developed in the last two decades inspired by the Brundtland Report (United Nations, 1987) that challenges future development to grow sustainably. Initiatives on closed-loop industrial cycles, for example by considering buildings as living organisms (‘Cradle-to-Cradle’, McDonough & Braungart, 2002), or biological inspiration for mimicking natural structures and processes to develop efficient and aesthetic innovative designed objects (‘Biomimicry’, Benyus, 2002), are just a few examples of these

revolutionary approaches. These perspectives are aimed at searching for energy efficiency, clean industrial production, product innovation and design methodology based on biological mechanisms and interactions of living things. However, the environment itself is not the topic of study of these approaches. As part of the same biological design approach, biophilic design is focused on environmental issues and psychological effects of nature on human’s well-being with special interest on how biophilic environments can provide people with restoration.

According to Beatley (2011) biophilia shows that the evolutionary and biological contact with nature cannot be avoided, even if people believe that life without nature is feasible. Janine Benyus (2008), the lead author of the biomimicry approach, points out that there is wisdom in bringing nature back into the building process by incorporating elements inspired by biophilia into the built environment. These elements include organic forms and structures, daylighting, natural ventilation, an environment quiet enough to enjoy natural sounds, a changing palette of colors, bringing working ecosystems indoors, and bio-inspiration gardens.

Biophilic Urban Spaces

An urban space is where the interactions between people and the urban environment occur producing a variety of different experiences (Jacobs, 1961; Gehl, 2010). The concept of urban place goes beyond the physical characteristics of the built environment. According to Macdonald (2011) the urban place is the public realm that needs to shift its direction in public values in order to take advantage of ecological opportunities that each particular environment may have. The concept of meaning is incorporated into the concept of urban space where thoughts, behaviors, activities, and life emerge and occur. The experience with the natural environment consists of views of nature and landscapes, whereas attitudes and emotions towards wildlife constitute part of this meaning (Gifford & McCunn, 2013), which in turn is related to the concepts of sense of place and place attachment.

Gifford (2007) suggests that it is important to define the city, the specific group, and tools to be used in order to study a place. The peculiarities of the natural and built environments make a huge difference in the outcomes expected from a specific site. One of the issues that urban environmental researchers are looking at is how natural environment and its complexity influence people’s well-being. An approach that takes advantage of these concepts in a positive fashion is therefore biophilic design (Wilson, 1984; Kellert et al., 2008). Biophilic design in urban places can help promote protect and strengthen favorable climate and microclimate conditions in cities (Beatley & Newman, 2013). A biophilic environment is about understanding the spirit and sensibilities of a built environment.

In the quest for principles of biophilic design, Benyus (2008) suggests a set of biophilic design elements inspired in nature: organic form and structure, daylighting, natural ventilation, natural sounds, a dynamic palette of colors, mimicking and

restorative landscapes, and bio-inspired gardens. Benyus (2008) proposes physical elements and processes from nature that can be applied to design products and artificial processes. The way in which animals and plants behave and adapt in wild environments are examples she uses to describe the considered restorative elements (Figure 1).

Kellert (2008) defines six elements and attributes that go from natural features to social relationships in cities. These elements consist of environmental features, natural shapes and forms, natural patterns and processes, light and space, place-based relationships, and evolved human-nature relationships (Figure 2). His proposal also incorporates a comprehensive study of the context that includes historical, geographical, and cultural components that affect individual's perceptions of the space and therefore the relationship of people with their affiliation to nature. Not all of these biophilic

design elements however constitute restorative components, but as they are part of the urban space, they affect to some extent mental restoration.

Using similar physical elements of nature to build the urban space, Bentley (2011) focuses on strategies for the integration of nature into the built environment. To do so, he proposes the following levels for the elements of biophilic design in the urban environment: building, block, street, neighborhood, community, and region. He argues that both political and social decision-makers should take part in the process of implementation of biophilic cities. This regional scale focuses on green elements and green urban spaces as components of a biophilic environment (Figure 3). Other biophilic components that provide restorative experiences such as diversity of color, daylight, natural water features, and organic structures, are not included in Bentley's proposal.

“A good place to settle: Biomimicry, Biophilia, and the Return of Nature's Inspiration to Architecture”

Organic forms and structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biomimic buildings Nature-inspired structures Restorative architecture Animal resilience to natural hazards
Daylighting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sunlight Windows and skylights Energy efficiency Darken or lighting flexibility
Natural ventilation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temperature control Humidity regulation Fresh air circulation
Natural sounds	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quiet places Avoidance of noise pollution
Palette of colors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relation to sun natural effect on color Natural brilliance Season flexible color palette
Mimicking and estorative landscape	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mimicking and restorative function Water storage and release Air and water purification Nutrient cycling Savannah type systems Bringing soil back
Bio-inspiration gardens	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ecosystem immersion Learning from organisms Design into nature Nature into built environment

Figure 1. Biophilic design elements inspired in Biomimicry (Benyus, 2008)

"Dimensions, Elements, and Attributes of Biophilic Design"

Environmental features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Color, water, and air Sunlight Plants and animals Natural materials Views and vistas; façade greening Geology and landscape; habitats and ecosystems Fire
Natural shapes and forms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Botanical and animal motifs Tree and columnar supports Shells and spirals, egg, oval, and tubular forms Arches, vaults, and domes Shapes resisting straight lines and right angles Simulation of natural features Biomorphy, geomorphology, and biomimicry
Natural patterns and processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sensory variability Information richness Age, change, and the patina of time Growth and efflorescence Central focal point Patterned wholes Bounded spaces and transitional spaces Linked series and chains Integration of parts to wholes Complementary contrasts Dynamic balance and tension Fractals Hierarchically organized ratios and scales
Light and space	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Natural light and shadow Filtered and diffused light; reflected light Light pools, warm light; light as shape and form Spaciousness, space as shape and form Spatial variability and harmony Inside-outside spaces
Place-based relationships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Historic, geographical, cultural and ecological connection to place Indigenous materials Landscape orientation and ecology Landscape features that define built form Integration of culture and ecology Spirit of place and avoiding placelessness
Evolved human-nature relationships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prospect and refuge; security and protection Order and complexity; information and cognition Curiosity and enticement; exploration and discovery Change and metamorphosis Mastery and control Affection and attachment; attraction and beauty Fear and awe Reverence and spirituality

Figure 2. Biophilic design elements and attributes (Modified from Kellert, 2008)

Figure 3. Biophilic green urban design elements in cities (Adapted from Beatley, 2011)

Biophilia focuses on natural elements to be incorporated into urban environments. From a psychological perspective, nature provides people with restorative experiences to overcome stress and mental fatigue that improve their health status. From an urban design perspective, nature provides aesthetics, shelter, and a sense of place (Jacobs, 1961; Register, 2010). The richness of biophilic design therefore stems from the combination of nature and urban design.

RESTORATION AND WELL-BEING AS A RESULT OF BIOPHILIC DESIGN

How nature helps improve health and well-being is in fact a historical topic of interest. A Greek text ‘Airs, waters and places’ by Hippocrates establishes the relationship among climate, geography, sun and heat, water quality, and a scenic environment that can be perceived by an individual and

the way in which these characteristics affect people’s health (Hippocrates, n/d; Steg et al., 2013). Weather conditions and their effects on people’s behavior are currently widely studied by social and environmental psychologists who suggest that the relationship between natural conditions and human well-being remains vital for people. It is important to mention that wildness and nature of the cities are not only related to green space. According to Beatley (2011), the use of trees on streets, courtyards, rooftops, creeks, and hydrological features should be considered and showed in cities rather than hiding them as is usual. The presence of nature also includes microorganisms, aquatic species, vegetation, and animals (Beatley, 2011, Register, 2010).

Even if a consensus about the effects of nature on people’s health exist, Gifford & McCunn (2013) argue that the effect of having nature indoors can be negative in terms of the productivity of workers. Although having plants in the office could increase people’s psychological health, these authors found that

having many plants could decrease people's labor productivity. Even though this paper is not focused in indoor spaces, it is clear however that other studies can provide insights about possible outcomes in different environments that need to be taken into account. The impact of nature on people's well-being, emotions, and health depends on the distance between the location of nature and people, and how biologically impoverished a particular environment is. However, an indirect contact of people with nature could be enough to have a restorative experience (Heerwagen & Orians, 1993). The use of windows with a green landscape view or even pictures of a preferred natural forest can improve human psychological conditions.

Restorative environmental design can be considered as a new design paradigm where a low-environmental impact strategy could avoid damage to the natural environment, and where a positive environmental impact, or biophilic design, brings benefits to human health (Kellert, 2008). There are two dimensions in this paradigm, an organic or naturalistic dimension, that includes shapes and forms in the built environment reflecting the intrinsic human affinity for nature (Wilson 1984; Kellert, 2008); and, a place-based or vernacular dimension that considers the culture and ecology of a specific geographical location that constitutes the social and ecological dimension of design (Papanek, 1984; Register, 2010).

The conditions of modern life decrease people's ability to keep focused on daily activities. However, the built environment can promote psychological health and well-being by also increasing social ties that facilitate recovery from mental fatigue. Mental fatigue can affect anxiety and depression, which in turn contribute to aggression and violence (Sullivan & Chang, 2011). The proximity to open green spaces in urban areas is associated with the reduction of stress levels. The way in which environmental settings are designed can produce positive or negative outcomes as suggested below (Table 1).

Social support and sense of community need to be addressed by design. Designers can promote social interaction within urban spaces and protect people from crowding that may cause stress and depression. They can do so by considering, for example, that living near heavy traffic is not a desired condition for commuters nor by neighbors, that high rise and multifamily housing may cause anxiety and depression, especially among children, or that the daylight is important to avoid seasonal affective disorder (Sullivan & Chang, 2011). Other facts include the following: the lack of quality in urban design can produce distress; drivers can experience road rage because of stress, as well as difficulties associated to the increasing length of the commutes. Cities need to reduce automobile commutes, prioritize walking and biking, and improve their quality of design that can be measured by the extent at which a city is legible. A legible city provides residents with a sense of emotional security as well as an invitation to explore it (Lynch, 1960; Kopec, 2006; Gifford, 2007; Sullivan & Chang, 2011).

Since the use of nature, that includes flora and fauna, improves people's health status and social aspects of life, the biophilic approach considers these natural elements in both the indoor and outdoor built environment in order to reconnect humans to nature. A restorative environment, as shown in several urban case studies and psychological experiments, can be provided with natural elements (see Table 1 above) such as vegetation and forest-like landscapes (Ulrich et al., 1991; Hartig et al., 2003; Groenewegen et al., 2006), natural water features such as wetlands, stormwater ponds, and rivers (Korpela et al., 2008; White et al., 2010; Faggi et al., 2013), natural light and its relation to color and shadows (Kaplan, 2001; Kopec, 2006), and built environments that include well designed buildings (Gifford & McCunn, 2013), the use of local materials, community identity, and edible gardens and parks (Beatley, 2011; Beatley & Newman, 2013).

FAVORABLE SETTINGS TO MENTAL HEALTH		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - legible places - attractive, well-maintained, safe places - contact with green space - with privacy - appropriate contact with other people 	Can produce	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - well-being - life satisfaction - quality of life - social support - ability to concentrate - creative play in children - less mental fatigue
UNFAVORABLE SETTINGS		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - crowded places - noisy places - dangerous places 	Can produce	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - social withdrawal - reduced social ties among neighbors - smaller social networks - diminished social and motor skills in children - distress - anxiety - irritability

Table 1. Favorable and unfavorable settings to mental health

Source: Modified from Sullivan & Chang, 2011.

Psychological restoration can also be a result of the benefits of recreation. Cole & Hall (2010) study the restorative effects of wilderness on people's well-being that is negatively impacted by urban stressors such as crowding, human density, and congestion. Their experiment in wilderness environments shows that the exposure of participants to nature results in restorative experiences, mental fatigue release, and mental rejuvenation. Moreover, Mayer et al. (2009) argue that brief exposures to nature can help people improve their ability to reflect on minor problems. The participants in this experiment were asked to think about minor issues to be solved and then reflect about them while walking in contact with nature during ten minutes. They point out that further research on the impact of different lengths of exposure to nature is needed in order to understand what people require to solve major issues.

According to Ulrich (1993; 2008), the understanding of the link between biophilic design and restorative effects needs more research. However, Gifford (2008) argues that the extensive evidence from environmental psychology, based on field and lab experiments, can constantly inform environmental design to provide spaces that address people's needs. Duffy & Verges (2010) also suggest that further research is required to explore people's connection to nature and the role of seasonal changes in nature for people's behavior. According to their study, people have a stronger identification with objects that provide shelter during winter, while they show a positive association with nature during spring and autumn. Moreover, prevalent activities in different seasons are associated with seasonal animals' behavior. For Duffy and Verges (2010), these studies cast doubt on the implicit and innate connection of people with nature or the 'biophilia hypothesis'. Gifford (2008) argues that natural hazards and other natural forces do not provide people with restorative effects; on the contrary, they produce biophobia at different levels, from phobia to bugs, to constant insecurity about natural disasters in vulnerable places. These arguments do not imply that restorative impacts of nature are wrong or inexistent, but that there exist positive and negative outcomes to be considered when working with nature, and that historical evidence on city development and the continuous search of people to be protected from extreme conditions of weather make sense.

Much of the organization of a society depends on the functioning of cities and even on how streets function in a daily basis (Jacobs, 1961). Economic, social, and individual outcomes are the result of well-designed urban spaces that include natural and built features (Gifford, 2007). At the personal level, material realizations, health status, social life, leisure time, security, and environmental quality constitute components of well-being. Urban residents become users of city amenities on a daily basis and, therefore, their levels of well-being depend to a large extent on what the city has to offer. Commuting time, walkability, and the scenic beauty of streets are just a few contributors to well-being. Whether city amenities increase or reduce the level of people's well-being should be the main concern of urban design.

CONCLUSION

People need to preserve nature and the health of ecosystems to maintain and improve their emotional health and well-being. It is ironic that urban designers seek to incorporate nature into built environments, because it is the built environment that was incorporated into nature in the first place, losing the well-known benefits of natural settings. On the other hand, however, the built environment provides urban residents with a more comfortable life by protecting them from environmental conditions and natural hazards. Urban spaces, in particular streets, should provide city residents with refuges and be designed by considering both the positive and negative outcomes from nature.

In order to improve people's mental health, environmental psychology and public health have provided enough evidence on the link between nature and well-being. The challenge for designers is to incorporate these theories and evidence into spaces where people live. Since the achievement of well-being is a public goal, the design of public spaces as restorative places should be urgently addressed by urban designers.

The components of the natural and built environment that provide psychological restoration are studied by environmental psychology. Restoration theories mentioned in this paper consider nature as a main element to improve people's mental health. The attention restoration theory requires fascination as a process to help release mental fatigue, whereas the stress recovery theory suggests that people can recover from stress because of an affective and aesthetic response to the environment. This paper highlights the strong relationship between the benefits of the natural environment, the required processes and responses of restorative theories, and the principles of biophilic design.

Biophilic design consists mainly of providing not only strategies but also a set of principles to design built environments. As shown throughout this paper, biophilic researchers have proposed elements and components, favorable settings, and space attributes to create better places for people's health. Further research on how these elements can help the restoration process, as well as the quality and quantity, and possible combinations of them in different public landscapes is needed. The effect of weather, seasonal characteristics, and environmental conditions on people's perception and experience of the environment in relation to restoration and well-being remains also an open question for future research.

The social dimension of people's behavior, mainly studied by environmental psychology, should be considered in biophilic strategies. Moreover, a comprehensive understanding on how the environment and people relate to each other may make the difference between a single solution with a blind angle, and a complex solution where interdisciplinary approaches can reduce risks in the proposal and implementation of urban design.

The results of research from different disciplines related to urban design are still not connected to each other. This is the

case, for instance, with the evidence on people's psychological health in urban spaces from environmental psychology and public health that has not been necessarily used by urban designers. The design of cities can take advantage of the research undertaken in disciplines other than urban design to incorporate, for example, biophilic design into the planning process at every stage. Biophilic design constitutes a promising field aimed at improving the design of cities to make a contribution to urban residents' well-being around the world.

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DESIGNING FOR POSITIVE EMOTION: LUDIC ARTIFACTS TO SUPPORT WELLBEING FOR PEOPLE WITH DEMENTIA

Dr. Cathy Treadaway

Cardiff Metropolitan University

✉ ctreadaway@cardiffmet.ac.uk

Dr. Gail Kenning

University of Technology Sydney

✉ gail@gailkenning.com

Steve Coleman

Cardiff Metropolitan University

✉ steve@steve-coleman.co.uk

ABSTRACT

This paper presents recent research investigating the development of playful artefacts to support the wellbeing of people with dementia. It describes the initial scoping phase of the research and draws from two funded projects: one in South Wales, UK, and the other in Sydney, Australia. The context for the study is explained and the global scale of the research problem defined. The benefits of playful activities across the life-course are identified, and the importance of hand uses, crafting, and creativity in later life are discussed. Research findings indicate that playful activities, particularly those that involve hand use, promote positive emotion and contribute to subjective wellbeing. These studies are being used to scope the design and development of ludic artefacts (age appropriate toys) for use in residential eldercare settings for people with dementia.

KEYWORDS: *Wellbeing, dementia, play, design, technology*

INTRODUCTION

The global challenge of an ageing population has yet to be fully embraced by the design community. The implications of the increase in numbers of old people affect not only the individual, (who potentially will be facing a decline of visual and auditory functioning, slowed reaction times, decline in motor skills and agility, and changes in cognitive processing), but also families, carers, health workers, eldercare facilities, social services and support networks, and medical and health systems. It will impact on the structure of the workforce, housing and infrastructure requirements, as well as national and international economic decision-making. Between 2000 and 2050 the proportion of the world's population over 60 years will double. The World Health Organisation has identified the challenge of caring for the elderly, especially those with dementia, to be made a public health priority at international and national levels (WHO, 2012). It states that enabling the ageing population to maintain healthy ageing and wellbeing is a social and economic imperative. Many people are able to age in good health and remain active participants in society, but others experience physical and cognitive limitations due to dementia

and may lose the ability to live independently. The number of people living with dementia worldwide is currently estimated at 35.6 million, this number will double by 2030, and more than triple by 2050 (WHO, 2012).

People living with dementia are amongst the most discriminated against groups of individuals who receive health and social care services (Health, 2012; Alliance, 2010). 'The language used in dementia care is frequently one of deficit, loss and behaviour management. Terms such as "elderly mentally infirm", "dementia sufferers", "geriatrics", "senility", "wanderers" are still in common use particularly in the popular press' (Andrews, 2013, p.1). These labels foster negative stereotypes of people who have little to offer or live for, and they have become a demographic that is frequently neglected by the design world.

Although ageing presents challenges to the individual and for society, it also presents opportunities for designers to creatively enhance life through socially responsible and appropriate design solutions. There exists a broad range of levels of independence and abilities of older members of the community, and particularly those with dementia. It is important not only to provide support for physiological needs but also to

maximize the potential for people to socialise, have fun, and enjoy their lives. This includes enabling interaction through play with other members of the ageing community, families including children, carers, and professional health workers. Research indicates that happy people live longer, retain their independence, and require less medication and social care (Huppert et al., 2005). There are personal, social, and economic benefits to finding new tools and strategies to promote positive emotion, social inclusion, and foster wellbeing in later life. The focus on *wellbeing* and *living well*, rather than physical and medical care, will be a challenge for many social care providers. Design solutions that can help support elderly people, especially those with dementia, to live well and enjoy life are urgently needed. The Design Council UK has recognised these design challenges as an emerging theme within their *Living Well with Dementia Design Challenge*. A number of design projects focused on designing to enhance the lives of PWD have been undertaken. These embrace a range of solutions including the design of artefacts, services, and technologies (Design Council 2012). The Design for Dementia project supported by the Royal College of Art and Helen Hamlyn Centre (Timlin, G. and Rysenbry, N., 2010), and socially aware projects at the Design Academy, Eindhoven (Cadamuro, A., 2014), are good examples of design research that is specifically addressing the needs of PWD. These projects identify the problems associated with designing for this demographic and add to the body of knowledge to inform future design. There is however, a clear need for appropriate design solutions that are not only concerned with *practical care* but that also consider *living well* and personal happiness.

Recent work by Desmet and Pohlmeier (2013, p.5) from the Delft Institute of Positive Design, advocates Positive Design as an appropriate design methodology to foster wellbeing. This approach encourages a shift in the design focus of new products away from *material* to more *personal values* that promote subjective wellbeing. Positive design methods are based on the principals of positive psychology and involve the explicit intention of designing to support human flourishing. The method takes account of pleasure, personal significance, and virtue as core design values.

The research described in this paper aims to contribute to this body of work. It seeks to address the spectrum of challenges facing the elderly, those with dementia, and their carers through the development of digitally augmented craft activities and age appropriate toys that will stimulate creative and playful experiences to support wellbeing. These will be devices to amuse, distract, comfort, engage, bring joy, and promote 'in the moment' living with the potential for social interaction or individual engagement for those with limitations due to memory loss or cognitive impairment.

Wellbeing

There is now a wide body of research to support the theory that creative activities are beneficial to wellbeing in older age and result in better health, fewer doctor visits, less medication usage, and increased activities and social engagement

(Hickson & Housley, 1997; Cohen et al., 2006; Cutler, 2009). In addition to the intrinsic and fundamental joys of creativity, artistic expression through traditional creative activities such as knitting, sewing, and painting provide opportunities for: 'personal fulfillment; the creation of meaning; lifelong learning; social linkages; celebration; communication; dignity and self esteem' (Cutler, 2009, p.13). Research undertaken for the Baring foundation identified the need for a new body of research into the positive wellbeing derived from participation in creative activities (Cutler, 2009).

Health and social care policy in the UK is currently going through a significant period of change. Legislation is being introduced to enhance the role of local authorities and health services and to set out overarching wellbeing duties for them and their partners. In 2010, the *National Dementia Declaration for England* captured outcomes that are needed to *live well* with the condition (Alliance, 2010) and the *Prime Minister's Challenge* expressed the need to build dementia friendly communities (Health, 2012). The focus on *wellbeing* and *living well*, rather than physical and medical care will be a challenge for many providers. Design solutions that can help support elderly people, especially those with dementia, to live well and enjoy life are urgently needed.

Playfulness and wellbeing

Playful activities have been found to support subjective wellbeing (Woodyer, 2012; Hannaford, 2010; Rogerson et al., 2013). The concept of using playfulness as a strategy for caring for people with dementia is becoming more widely accepted in the UK and Australia (Killick, 2013b). Findings from the authors' previous research have highlighted differences between what is considered by society as 'play', and those activities that are 'playful' (Rogerson et al., 2013). It has been proven that it is the ludic, intrinsic *playfulness* in leisure activities that are able to reduce stress and support wellbeing. However, in cultures and society where there is a strong work ethic, playful activities are often considered a waste of time and money, serving no useful purpose. Play is often regarded as a form of resistance (as in 'playing around' or 'playing up') and has negative connotations which place it diametrically opposed to work (Kane, 2005). Play is the preserve of children and, with maturity, is put aside in order to attain adulthood. While society grants permission to play specifically to children, this permission is inhibited in adult life. An alternative view proposes that playing is an innate human characteristic, which is useful throughout the course of life (Dissanayake, 2000). Where self-permission for adults is granted, for instance through hobbies and leisure activities, ludic playfulness has been shown to support subjective wellbeing, encouraging living in the moment, absorption and providing new mental spaces that stimulate imaginative thinking. These activities provide new ways of 'being in the world' that are non-goal orientated and open (Woodyer, 2012). They enable life to be lived more intensely since they rely on sensory experience and openness to the world, eliciting a combination of cognitive and 'felt' responses.

Older adults frequently find themselves isolated and disconnected from their communities, or unable to engage with others as a result of issues relating to physical and mental health, anxiety, or lack of mobility. Previous research indicates that social interaction and a sense of belonging in society are vital to subjective wellbeing (Huppert et al., 2005). Playfulness also supports ways of socially engaging with others through shared play spaces, either physical or imaginary.

The research described in this paper uses theories of relationship-centered care (Nolan et al., 2003) to scope the development of new craft based activities and artefacts using emerging technologies that enable and promote open-ended, non-goal orientated *ludic* play to support wellbeing. Killick (2013a) argues that dementia should be regarded more as a disability than a medical condition. He contends that since dementia impacts significantly on interpersonal relationships that we have a ‘crucial task in helping people to create the atmosphere in which dementia flourishes’ (Ibid., p.13). The focus of the design challenge is, therefore, to develop designs that stimulate positive emotion, bring happiness, laughter, and joy in both an individual and social context.

The concepts of playfulness, fun, and laughter fly in the face of negative stereotypes and attitudes towards dementia, and to date there has been little research into positive emotions (such as pleasure and happiness) and their impact on wellbeing within eldercare settings (Cohen-Mansfield et al., 2012). There is, however, research evidence to suggest that the areas of the brain that are least affected by dementia are those associated with imagination, feelings, and emotions (Zeisel, 2011). It seems likely, therefore that activities that utilise these brain regions may have potential to provide stimulation and engagement for a person even when memory is impaired. Advances in neuroscience have evidenced that laughter is a deeply embedded behaviour in humans and that it has a very important role in supporting social connectivity and sense of belonging (Scott, 2013).

Memory and emotion

The research described in this paper seeks to identify ways to stimulate memory and engage, distract, and to calm people with dementia (PWD), for whom life is increasingly frustrating and limiting. Dementia is an incurable condition, which encompasses a range of neurodegenerative conditions: ‘symptoms can include severe memory loss, mood and personality changes and behaviors that challenge others such as serious confusion, agitation and aggression’ (Alliance, 2010, p.2).

A number of studies involving memory and reminiscence with PWD in conjunction with museums and art galleries have shown that handling objects and viewing art can be therapeutic (Kendall, 2013). Eldercare homes often use artefacts, or even whole rooms decorated in period style filled with appropriate objects, in order to stimulate residents’ memory. There is evidence that these forms of intervention can be very stimulating and bring pleasure to residents (Ibid.). For some PWD however, reminiscing can be difficult and may reinforce a sense of loss, or evoke negative and painful emotions. Ac-

tivities that promote flourishing and positive emotion are often those that are *of the moment*, engage the senses, and provide self-esteem or personal fulfillment. Creative activities such as art and craft, dance and music have been found to provide this kind of in the moment living and can be very uplifting (Cutler, 2009; Hickson & Housley, 1997). However, as the condition deteriorates, the potential to engage in such activities becomes increasingly limited. Development of new approaches to engage in creative activities and new types of artefacts to be used with PWD in the later stage of the condition are desperately needed, especially those that might facilitate continued social interaction.

One approach that is being investigated is how different memory systems in the brain might be used to unlock different kinds of memories: emotional and procedural. Ledoux (1998) contends that the brain has multiple memory systems devoted to different kinds of learning and memory functions. According to Ledoux, *conscious recollection* (declarative or explicit memory), is the general meaning of the word *memory* in everyday conversation; it implies bringing to mind past experience and describing it verbally. However, other deep *emotional* (implicit) memories are stored in the brain and provide a trace of unconscious responses to experience. The brain subconsciously evaluates experience, deciding whether it is to be ignored or if it should lead to some physical reaction (such as sensing danger and then preparing for fight or flight). These reactions result in the stimulation of the autonomic nervous system and can be evidenced physically in changes in heart rate and sweat gland activity. Appraisal or conscious evaluation of experience is often accompanied by awareness by the individual of the internal body response, which then results in the *feeling* of the emotion (Damasio, 2000). The speed of this is so fast that it is perceived to be concurrent with the experience and this may go some way to explaining gut reaction and intuition. There is evidence that co-activation of *conscious* memory can be assisted by *emotional* memory systems during remembering (LeDoux, 1998, p.213). The content of memory is also influenced by emotional experience, and unpleasant memories are more likely to be remembered when we are sad and pleasant ones when we are happy. These insights suggest that it might be possible to tap into these deeper implicit memory systems when access to explicit and verbalised conscious memory declines.

Physical (bodily and dexterous) activities that have been practiced over many years become encoded in the brain as procedural memory that is tacit and outside conscious recollection (Sennett, 2008). Craft skills, music making, and dance present good examples of such activities. It is possible that these different memory systems may help inform new ways to approach designing for people with dementia.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The next section of the paper describes two studies that have been used to gather data about the kinds of activities that PWD currently engage in, and their impact on wellbeing. Two

recent projects are described, one in the UK and one in Australia, in order to scope requirements for the design of novel ludic artefacts to support positive wellbeing for people with dementia. Both have used ethnographic qualitative research methodologies: interviews, focus groups, and participatory workshop sessions, to gather data about caring for people with dementia in residential care as well as wider issues concerning the ageing process and hand crafting activities.

SIP visits and OPAN workshops

‘Making a Difference’ was a research project led by Dr. Cathy Treadaway, funded by Welsh Assembly Government and Higher Education Funding Council for Wales’ (HEFCW) Strategic Insight Programme (SIP), and Older People and Ageing Research and Development Network (OPAN). The aim of the research was to investigate how the subjective wellbeing of PWDs in residential care might be supported through playful activities. The first study involved a series of visits to eldercare homes and specialist dementia units to meet with staff including managers, occupational therapists, and carers, as well as people with dementia. The visits provided a clear picture of the context in which the designs might be used, and highlighted the many issues that face staff caring for people with dementia, as well as the spectrum of challenges that they encounter in daily life within a care home environment. In particular this research identified a clear need for age appropriate toys to be used in residential eldercare settings. Managers commented on the concerns expressed by relatives who felt that the children’s toys being given to residents were ‘inappropriate’ despite the apparent benefits to the individual elderly person. Although the managers prioritised the PWD’s needs, rather than the relatives’ opinions, they expressed concern that there was a gap in the market for age appropriate toys that stimulate and engage. In addition to this, carers and managers also identified a need for activities that would stimulate social interaction, communication, and physical movement. Occupational therapists also highlighted difficulties experienced at particular points in the day when caring for PWDs in residential care, for example at bath time and bedtime. It was felt that anything that could be designed

to provide a distraction or enticement to encourage residents at these times would be hugely beneficial in reducing stress for both residents and staff. Managers explained that there was an apparent correlation between residents’ falls (often with hospital admission) and stress levels amongst PWD and staff. Designs that could help mitigate this would not only relieve individual suffering but also have a beneficial economic impact.

This preparatory research enabled strong relationships to be developed with the eldercare provider, Gwalia Cyf, and led to the appointment of a fully funded research student who is currently working on a doctoral study as part of the project.

As a consequence of this scoping, research funding was awarded to assist the formation of a focus group, comprising care professionals, occupational therapists, eldercare home managers, medical clinicians, representatives of charities, academics, and researchers who had a shared interest in the development of age appropriate toys. Three workshops were funded by OPAN in order to develop a research proposal and explore the research territory. Each workshop event focused on key areas to be examined in the research:

- Playfulness and dementia
- Haptic sensibilities and touch
- Technology and smart materials

Experts in the field facilitated the workshops’ stimulating discussions and led practical activities with the group. These activities included participatory games, playful visualisation, and ideation exercises using Lego® and children’s construction toys as well as *post it note* brainstorming and similar techniques. Each session was video recorded for analysis, and participants completed feedback sheets in order to gather views and ideas.

Crafting Wellbeing

The *CRAFTING WELLBEING: An exploration of the relationship between craft-based textiles and health and wellbeing* was a study conducted in 2013 in Sydney, Australia. Focusing on craft-based textile activities, such as knitting, crochet, and

Figure 1. OPAN workshop

lace making, the research examined how creative or playful intrinsically motivated activities contribute to health and wellbeing. The investigation was carried out by Dr Gail Kenning, University of Technology (UTS), Sydney, Australia at the Lace Study Centre (LSC); at the Powerhouse Museum (PHM) in Sydney; and the Epping Craft Centre (ECC), New South Wales (NSW), Australia. Sixteen women between the ages of 45 and 90 took part in a series of unstructured interviews between 40 and 75 minutes long. While all of those interviewed had made lace, the majority did not confine themselves to lace making, but engaged in a wide range of textile activities. A growing body of self-reporting by craft practitioners in books and on websites attests to the importance of craft-based textile activities and suggests that craft activities have helped practitioners through times of loneliness, adversity, and illness (Vercillo, 2012). In addition, independent research studies are corroborating long-held anecdotal views regarding the positive effects of, for example, knitting, crochet, tatting, and lacemaking, for general health and positive wellbeing (Schofield-Tomschin, 2001; Jenkins et al., 2013). Therefore this research aimed to engage craft-practitioners in a series of interviews in an effort to find out whether these activities contributed to their sense of wellbeing and in what way; in effect, *how*, did they contribute to their positive wellbeing. The interviews began by simply asking makers how they began their craft activity, who taught them, when, and what was the activity. The ‘conversation’ was then allowed to develop, enabling a wide range of topics to be introduced by the interviewees.

Craft-based textile activities are frequently acknowledged as being social and communal practices, and so practitioners benefit from the effects on general health and wellbeing brought about through social interaction. Findings from the *Crafting Wellbeing* project supports this position, with many participants talking about the importance of the friends they have made as a result of being part of the knitting, sewing, or lacemaking group. However, craft-based textile activities seemingly positively contribute to health and wellbeing in a number of other ways. These include, but are not limited to, providing both physical and cognitive challenges; positive self-identification; respect of peers; company during times of solitude; a sense of association with larger textile communities and practices, both historically and geographically; and a reminder of skills learned and achievements gained (Kenning, 2013). In addition, craft practitioners frequently highlighted the importance of the process and the *act of making*. Although the making process culminated in the production of an object, many of them did not undertake the activity with a focus on the end product; the creative activity itself gave them a sense of achievement and pride in what they had made. While some practitioners gained comfort from ensuring that their hands were busy, often making reference to the perceived risks associated with ‘idle hands’, others celebrated a sense of rhythm, pace, and tempo arising out of the making process, and the tactility of ‘fiddling with threads’ (Kenning, 2013). Without exception, in this study all participants made reference to an emotional connection to

Figure 2. Lace makers engaging in intrinsically motivated activities, part of the *Crafting Wellbeing* study

this form of making. This took the form of memories of family members, friends or mentors who taught them; hopes for the future that they may teach grandchildren or friends textile processes or techniques; the sense of connectedness that they felt towards their local craft community or to the history of their particular form of craft activity; or the joy at being able to achieve. In the retelling and recounting of their experiences, makers lay claim to emotional experiences that in actuality may have been less intense at the time. Nevertheless, in these cases it would seem that positive reflection in itself seemingly contributes to positive wellbeing, however transiently. Craft-based textile activities are intrinsically motivated, and frequently carried out for the pleasure gained from engaging in the activity. The research found that craft-practitioners were happy to talk about their experiences and the joy of making, and from this we might draw parallels between the subjective wellbeing arising out of play.

DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

The two projects described in the previous section have provided insights into the types of activities currently used in eldercare facilities, and amongst groups of older people and how these support their wellbeing. Both studies found that physical dexterity, as well as the various progressive stages of dementia place limitations and constraints on the scope of the research. Stakeholder groups including older people and professional carers, have contributed their knowledge and expertise about the condition, suggesting ideas for designing activities and products to support PWD. The two projects have highlighted the value of activities that are in the moment, creative and fun. Findings indicate that activities that involve the hands are particularly successful in supporting wellbeing in older adults. The Australian study has identified that intrinsic motivation and haptic sensibilities promote wellbeing through the life course and the act of remembering the pleasure of past making activities promotes positive emotion. The UK study has highlighted the need for activities that can replace the more intricate manipulative elements of

crafting but retain the rhythms and movements that are ludic, and that bring pleasure and sensory satisfaction.

Haptics and hand use

The intrinsic reward that motivates craft practitioners stems, at least in part, from satisfaction derived from hand use and making. Dissanayake (2000) contends that making by hand fulfills an innate human need and that the rhythms and flows, that repetitive crafting processes require, draw from a deep emotional knowledge. The connection between crafting by hand and emotional wellbeing has been shown to be associated with total immersion in an activity in a *flow* state (Csikszentmihalyi, 1996) and a deep physical pleasure from working with the hands (Treadaway, 2009). Older people, who have engaged in craft practice throughout their lives and for whom the skills of making are deeply embedded in procedural memory, are supported emotionally through the activity. This iterative cycle of physical dexterous repetition and emotional reward is combined with a sense of achievement and social connectivity (Yatczak, 2011). Craft activities adhere to the rules of construction (forming a stitch or following a pattern) but can also be ludic and playful (making for the sheer joy of making), as well as being purposeful and goal orientated. Anecdotal evidence from a participant in the OPAN research, described earlier, suggests that people in the later stages of dementia continue to be able to practice handcraft such as knitting, although their competence at following a pattern may decline. The rhythmic and repetitive manual activity is deeply embedded in implicit procedural memory. This area will be explored further in future research to examine how the rhythms and tacit knowledge from handcrafting could be integrated in design concepts.

Play and Technology

Technology and smart materials now provide huge potential for developing new kinds of devices that are able to augment traditional crafting processes with technology (Minuto & Nijholt, 2013). Many designers working for this demographic are utilising wireless technologies and mobile devices: mobile phones and iPads provide assistive technologies for eldercare staff and residents (Blythe et al., 2010; Maiden et al., 2013; Lindsay, 2012). One of the problems integrating technologies within a care home environment is limited staff time and availability (Maiden et al., 2013). Another issue for PWD is memory, and the obvious difficulties in remembering how to use a device. Projects have successfully overcome this issue through intergenerational support that encourages young people to use a device in collaboration with the older person (Blythe et al., 2010). Ideally, however, devices made for PWD need to be intuitive, pleasurable to handle and enable both individual and social play without the necessity for a tech savvy assistant or carer.

The next stage of the research will require input from a range of stakeholders to capture the specific requirements and specifications of activities and devices to be designed. An

inclusive participatory design method is proposed in which researchers, developers and users will come together in a series of workshop events to originate experimental digital devices that are intuitive, tactile, and playful. These will be things to touch, hold, and manipulate (fiddle with) that have no specific purpose other than their intrinsic ludic enjoyment – they will be for playful playing. Engagement of PWD with these new playful interfaces will be documented through qualitative case study methods and evaluated for their impact on positive emotion and mental wellbeing.

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PSYCHOLOGICAL DISTRESS AND WELL-BEING IN PROSTHETIC USERS

THE ROLE OF REALISM IN BELOW-KNEE PROSTHESES

Stefania Sansoni

✉ stefania.sansoni@strath.ac.uk

ABSTRACT

The needs of below-knee amputees, in terms of the aesthetics of their prostheses, receive little or no attention. Failure to address this issue could create dissatisfaction with the body image of amputees. This paper seeks to explore different aspects of the psychological issues and well-being of users by focusing on the hypothesis that the level of realism in prostheses is linked to multiple factors, i.e. the time elapsed since amputation and acceptance of limb loss. Specifically, we highlight the positive role of using artificial-looking devices for promoting the self-confidence of wearers during the second phase post-amputation, and the use of cosmetic devices in the first phase. The data derives from a closed ended questionnaire, email exchanges with users and an in-depth literature review. The paper constitutes a contribution to research on the “aesthetics of prosthetic devices” by taking into account the dynamics behind the psychological distress and well-being of prosthetic users.

KEYWORDS: prosthetic devices, aesthetics, well-being, body image, lower limb amputees

INTRODUCTION

This paper explores the role of realism in prostheses as a way of meeting the expectations of prosthetic users at two stages post-amputation, and how wearing the “right” design (according to the perception of the amputee observer) can positively affect body image and self-esteem. Specifically, we argue for the positive role played by non-realistic prostheses in enhancing psychological well-being.

“Prosthetic” is a term that refers to devices designed to replace a missing part of the body. This definition applies to devices that replace a limb segment rather than externally-applied devices which are referred to as “orthotics”. For example, an artificial arm, leg, or finger can be classified as a “prosthesis”, whereas external entities such as a dental brace, insoles or a pair of glasses are “orthotics”. Specifically, our field of research currently focuses on below-knee prosthetic devices. In this paper we will refer to any device resembling the appearance of a human leg with the term “cosmetic” (Figures 1a and 1b), while the terms “non-cosmetic”,

“non-realistic” or “artificial looking” will be used identify devices with an interface dissimilar to a human leg (Figures 1c and 1d).

The subjects of our research are amputees [or rather people who have had a limb amputated (Pearsall, 1999)] who are prosthetics users or future users. For the specific purposes of this paper we refer to below-knee amputees, even though the sample does include a few examples of upper limb wearers.

The limited literature on the aesthetics of prosthetic devices demonstrates that this field is still in its infancy. A review of current prosthetic design literature shows that to date extended work has been largely focused on the technical improvement of the devices (Cheetham, Suter, & Jäncke, 2011; Hahl, Taya, & Saito, 2000; Klute, Kallfelz, & Czerniecki, 2001; Mak, Zhang, & Boone, 2001) in spite of the research around aesthetics. Our search found few academic studies discussing realistic-appearance prosthetic devices- and that the literature that does exist focuses mainly on upper limb designs (Davies, Douglas, & Small, 1977; Ferrone, 2001). This contrasts with a considerable number of companies (e.g. “Pro-

Figure 1: cosmetic devices with high (a) and medium (b) level of human resemblance (sources: (a) The Alternative Limb Project, photographer: Rosemary Williams - www.thealternativelimbproject.com - (b) photo from personal archive), and “non-cosmetic” or “artificial looking” devices (c and d) (sources (c) The Alternative Limb Project, photographer: Rosemary Williams - www.thealternativelimbproject.com - (d) “Ecko Unltd. Prosthetic Leg” of Jordan Diatlo - <http://www.jordandiatlo.com>)

cosil”, “Touch Bionics”, “The alternative Limb project”, “Otto-bock”) and associations (i.e. “Amputee Coalition”, “Amputee prosthetics”, “Westcoast brace and limbs”) that deal with the production and/or advertisement of high-level realistic-looking limbs. Similarly, we found little literature investigating the aesthetics of non-realistic devices (Capestany & Esparza, 2011; Hilhorst, 2004; Plettenburg, 2005), but wider attention on the part of companies (e.g. “The alternative Limb project”, “Bespoke innovations”) and designers (i.e. Sophie de Oliveira Barata, Scott Summit).

METHOD

The main data-sources used to prepare this paper consist of responses to a questionnaire, personal e-mails from below-knee prosthetic users and a comprehensive literature review.

Regarding the internet survey, the study consisted of an online questionnaire (that took approximately 25 minutes to complete). It was based on a set of closed ended questions structured using the Likert scale rating system. A quantitative method was adopted because of the necessity of collecting a large amount of data. There were one hundred and fourteen participants in the study who may be classified as follows:

- Amputation: Amputees 24 (21.1%) and Non-amputees 90 (78.9%)
- Gender: 40.4% Male and 59.6% Female

Amputee participants were sub-classified into: lower limb amputees 22 (92%) and upper limb amputees 2 (8%).

The International Personality Item Pool (IPIP) template was chosen for testing personality aspects (L. R. Goldberg et al., 2006). This system provides a list of questions for investigating the personality traits of participants. Each question offered participants the opportunity to rate the statement, choosing one of the five points on the Likert scale between “very inaccurate” and “very accurate”. The scoring had to be

evaluated as “positive” or “negative” according to the statement proposed. The issues investigated were: level of physical activity, extroversion and assertiveness, sociability, calmness, courage, kindness, and generosity. Each of these traits was tested by posing an average of 10 questions.

Regarding the e-mail based data collection, the information was gained through informal conversations engaged in with prosthetic users between 2012 and 2013.

PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF PROSTHETIC USERS

The amputation of a limb can generate unpleasant psychological consequences (R. T. Goldberg, 1984; Horgan & MacLachlan, 2004; Price & Fisher, 2007; Rybarczyk, Nyenhuis, Nicholas, Cash, & Kaiser, 1995; Shukla, Sahu, Tripathi, & Gupta, 1982; Whyte & Niven, 2001) in addition to profound effects on body image (Maguire & Parkes, 1998). Specifically, the literature shows how dealing with the new bodily dissatisfaction can generate symptoms such as stress and depression (Breakey, 1997; Cansever, Uzun, Yildiz, Ates, & Atesalp, 2003; Williamson, Schulz, Bridges, & Behan, 1994), difficulty in accepting an amputation (Sjödahl, Gard, & Jarnlo, 2004) and problems establishing romantic and sexual relationships (C. Murray, 2009). In some cases it has been shown that an amputee experiences extreme denial. English (1989) records the example of a woman amputee who “had even left instructions in her will that she should be buried in her artificial leg so that even beyond the grave her secret would be preserved”.

Breakey (1997) argues that, despite the existence of psychological issues influencing psychological well-being and life satisfaction in amputees, the rehabilitation process pays little attention to these problems in patients. Additionally, Asano et al. (2008) state that, according to their scale, lower limb amputees record lower quality of life scores than upper limb amputees.

The literature shows that the physical trauma of amputation can have negative psychological repercussions in amputees, and we argue that it is important to account for this if the prosthetic users are to be better understood.

Surprisingly, in addition to these examples illustrating the negative issues associated with amputation, it has also been shown that positive post-amputation experiences exist. Many experts in the field, including medical staff, tend to conceive of amputation as a “mutilating” procedure, while other researchers see the issue in a positive light, as a process of reconstruction (Bowker, 1981; Bradway, Malone, Racy, Leal, & Poole, 1984). Stress is one of the main consequences of limb amputation. However it has been argued that when this aspect is overcome, it can have a positive outcome as the self-esteem of the amputee can be “strengthened and grown” [(Ickovics & Park, 1998), in (Oaksford, Frude, & Cuddihy, 2005a)]. Similarly, Bonanno (2004) describes the experience of coping with adversity (i.e. amputation) as an opportunity to thrive and change. In accordance with this belief, Gallagher and Maclachlan (2001) report an interview with an amputee who states she’s feeling “great” because she managed to “get on with her life” by dealing successfully with the trauma and now feels like “a better person”.

Tedeschi et al. (1996) state that the experience of thriving after a traumatic experience is named “posttraumatic growth” and that this process is obtained by a change in how people view themselves (Tedeschi & Calhoun, [1996, 2004]), cited in Phelps et al. (2008), when others highlight the importance of “meaning-making” for successfully overcoming the post-traumatic experience (Taylor, 1983). Phelps et al. (2008) argue that the core process of thriving positively with amputation consists in engaging a set of cognitive coping strategies such as revising life goals and priorities if the traumatic experience is to be overcome. An amputee mentioned in Gallagher and Maclachlan (2001) stated that the acceptance of amputation is an important issue in the process of getting over the experience [the psychological dissatisfaction]: “it is like when somebody you know dies, it takes a while to get over it, but gradually you do”.

In accordance with the literature, our questionnaire shows that amputees (compared with non-amputee participants) recorded a significantly higher “positive level of traits” showing a “positive attitude towards life” such as: physical activity, extroversion (or assertiveness), sociability, bravery (or courage), and generosity. Our understanding of the psychological process post-amputation is that amputees, after facing the natural process of negative psychological reactions, can respond to psychological distress and reach a positive life-facing attitude, even gaining higher levels than non-amputees. We claim that both negative and positive psychological feelings in amputees are part of their normal process of “growth” and that these can be directly related to prosthetic design choices. Consequently, gaining a clear comprehension of these dynamics is essential if the role of the aesthetics of devices for wearers is to be understood. This belief will be explored further in the following sections.

The grieving process post-amputation

In “psychological adaption to amputation”, Bradway et al. (1984) argue for the existence of one pre-amputation stage (which may not occur in certain cases) and three post-amputation stages, which is universally experienced. The stages are a) grief b) realization that the limb is no longer present c) denial and d) return home. The authors state that denial is the stage where people tend to show negative psychological symptoms (depression, insecurity, worry, etc.) (Friedmann, 1978; Parkes, 1975), and that the phase of returning home can generate either a successful adaption to disability or, sadly, a “fall” back to the previous stage.

The prosthetic web site “Hanger” describes amputation as a life-changing experience that may be emotionally devastating. “Everyone deals with these feelings in different ways. Allow yourself to grieve and to feel your loss. [...] Ultimately, you will reach a stage of acceptance. How long this may take varies from person to person but one thing is certain: when you are able to accept your new body image you’ll be able to lead a happier life.”

“The Five Stages of the Grieving Process” have been identified as a set of psychological stages that people go through when experiencing amputation: denial, anger, bargaining, depression, acceptance and hope (Kubler-Ross, 2009). This process is discussed by the amputee researcher Saul Morris (in “Amputee Coalition”) and is described as “essential” because anyone who has ever experienced an amputation goes through the same cycle, though the duration of each stage varies according to the individual (“some people will do it in a short time, while others will take several months”).

Rybarczyk et al. (1995), show that depression in amputees can be classified both in the long term (17 years after amputation) and in the short term (4 years after amputation). This finding suggests that the grieving process may not necessarily end with “acceptance and hope” and therefore the stages may not hold true for everyone, or that “acceptance and hope” may take even longer than 17 years after amputation.

The role of prosthetic devices in the psychological well-being of prosthetic users

“No-one comes out unscathed by an amputation and a prosthesis may act as a security, a guarantee or a mechanism for requiring the integrity of one’s physical appearance, which validates one’s psychological integrity.” (Pillet & Didierjean-Pillet, 2001)

For some time now researchers have been interested in the enhancement of self-body image and psychological well-being of amputees. Singh, Hunter and Philip (2007) emphasize the benefits of learning new skills and improving the mobility of the amputee in order to overcome unpleasant psychological feelings. Similarly, Dunn (1996) focuses on: 1) finding positive meaning in being an amputee, 2) adopting an optimistic attitude and 3) perceiving control over disability. In the context of dealing with phantom limb pain (an issue

that negatively affects the physical and psychological well-being of amputees), it has been argued that factors such as, for example, the individual patient's medical history, phantom sensations, daily activities, social support received and the influence of an amputation has to be taken into account when analyzing improvements in an amputee's well-being (Bosmans et al., 2007).

A functional prosthesis may undoubtedly be considered an important contribution to achieving well-being. For example, it has been argued that the use of a prosthesis helps the user to regain mobility (Pohjolainen, Alaranta, & Kärkäinen, 1990) and to return to performing social activities (C. D. Murray, 2005). However, by going beyond the functional role of the prosthesis, the literature shows how the aesthetics of the device influence the psychological concerns of amputees. It has been argued that if users are to accept a prosthesis it must be comfortable, functional and have a pleasant appearance (Millstein, Heger, & Hunter, 1986). Similarly, Bhuvaneshwar et al. (2007) report that "cosmetic appearance appears to play as great a role in psychological sequel of amputation as does the return of physical function". Similarly, Murray (2005) reports the case of a prosthetic user who refuses to wear his prosthesis on a daily basis, providing as an explanation the judgment that the device is "clumsy and unattractive" rather than a specific complaint regarding functionality. Similarly, Nguyen (2013), and Rybarczyk and Behel (2008) address the fact that adjustment difficulties in amputees should be reconnected to the aesthetics of the limb by highlighting the importance of this kind of aesthetic dissatisfaction for females.

From a design perspective, Cairns, Murray et al. (2013) argue that the appearance of the prosthesis affects acceptance of the device and that there is a link between the perception of its negative aesthetics and a negative self-body image. In the context of lower limb cosmetic devices, the argument goes that the improvement of the aesthetics of the prosthesis can consequently help to improve the self-body image and psychological wellbeing of the wearer. Accordingly, it is our belief that the aesthetics of prosthetics can influence the psychological well-being of lower-limb amputees and we argue that this principle should be accounted for in prosthetic design.

Considering the role of hand prostheses, Pillet and Didierjean-Pillet (2001) argue that the device can be the "answer" to overcoming the issues encountered when taking part in social activities. The authors also highlight the fact that all amputees have special personal requirement and that "nowadays, function is not sought at any cost, especially not at the cost of sacrificing the appearance of the hand". Regarding the use of digital cosmetic prostheses (i.e. devices with a high level of limb-like realism – Figure 1a), Carrol and Fyfe (2004) state that in contrast to PVC prostheses (devices with a lower level of limb-like realism – Figure 1b), they can reduce the level of anxiety and depression in the wearer. Their conclusion is that the "improvement" of the realistic appearance of devices can enhance the well-being of users. We find ourselves discordant with the positive effect of the level of realism in prostheses, but we agree with these authors concern-

ing the importance of pleasant aesthetics in helping resolve psychological distress in amputees.

The limitation that we found in the works cited up till now is that they take into account only the aesthetic role of cosmetic prostheses. Few academic papers have focused on the non-cosmetic aesthetics of prosthetic design when it comes to improving the experiences of the wearers, suggesting that this research gap is relatively new and unexplored. An example of literature which does briefly touch upon the subject is provided by authors such as Capestany and Esparza (2011) who describe a case study of an amputee who required a personalized golf-prosthesis. In a similar manner, Plettenburg (2005) designed a prosthetic prehensor (a design similar to a wrench) for children, by using a combination of solid design and an appealing colorful style. Similarly, Hilhorst (2004) described his non-conformist-styled design applied to prostheses for children, personalizing them for each individual's unique "identity". These three examples are significant in terms of exploring the role of non-cosmetic-looking devices intended to enhance the well-being of individuals. Our research differs in that it examines both cosmetic and non-cosmetic designs and that it focuses on lower limb devices rather than upper limbs.

Regarding upper limb amputees, Pillet (2001) proposes the question "can a patient who abandons his/her prostheses be considered healed?". According to our point of view, in upper limb prosthetic users this stage of acceptance of the new body could be verified if the amputee chooses to use a non-cosmetic device or to abandon the use of prosthetics altogether. As a matter of fact, the difference between upper and lower limb amputees is that the use of a prosthetic leg may be required if mobility is to be regained, or the individual is to be able to take part in social activities; in these cases arm/hand prostheses mainly represent an aesthetic "security" (Pillet, 1984). However, considering that this paper focuses on lower limb prosthetic users, we will not go into this issue in greater depth here.

LEVELS OF REALISM IN PROSTHESES REFLECTING THE ACCEPTANCE OF AMPUTATION

Our opinion is that the achievement of well-being for amputees is not a simple goal but is linked to internal dynamics and external events correlated to the trauma of the amputation. Additionally, all individuals have a personal story and the track for achieving well-being may vary from case to case. However, it is our belief that a set of general dynamics may potentially be present in all subjects. In addition to the important role of issues such as the rehabilitation process, medical treatment, social support, etc., the role played by the aesthetics of prosthetics can make a valid contribution that enhances well-being in amputees by improving their self-body image.

In this section we introduce our hypothesis regarding the role of realism in the aesthetics of prostheses in enhancing acceptance

Figure 2. Graph showing the two phases experienced by prosthetic users for the desirable level of realism in the prostheses related to influencing factors - Phase 1: the amputated body is not accepted and the preference is for cosmetic devices, Phase 2: positive acceptance of amputation and attraction of non-cosmetic devices

during the post-amputation stages, with an additional focus on other factors involved (i.e. time and coping strategies).

First, we propose a simplistic division of the post-amputation period into two stages: the first characterized by strong unpleasant psychological feelings (“Phase one”) correlated with the fact that the limb loss is not accepted yet, and the second stage during which a positive attitude towards life emerges as a consequence of a greater acceptance of amputation (“Phase two”). Second, we aim to correlate an overview of the aesthetic needs of prosthetic users in order to determine a desirable level of realism in the prostheses (Figure 2).

We understand the psychological process during the post-amputation period to be far more complex and that it may normally include more than two phases. However, in order to meet the specific requirements of this research, we decided to simplify the post-amputation stage and to focus only on the factors of non-acceptance [i.e. grouping the first four phases of the “grieving process”: denial, anger, bargaining, and depression (Kubler-Ross, 2009)] and acceptance [i.e. the last phase of the “grieving process”: acceptance and hope (Kubler-Ross, 2009)].

The main factors affecting the phases of the graph are Time, Level of Acceptance of Amputation, and Personal Characteristics (gender, age, self-consciousness). The first and second factors (Time and Level of Acceptance) will be described first, after which we will deal with Personal Characteristics.

Time

Sprangers and Schwartz (1999) suggest that the internal standards of amputees are re-defined over time, and that psychological adaptation occurs in a parallel process (Gallagher & MacLachlan, 2001; Livneh, Antonak, & Gerhardt, 1999; Pezzin, Dillingham, & MacKenzie, 2000). Additionally,

it has been stated that coping strategies change over time simultaneously with the changing demands of adjustment (Lazarus, 2006 cited in Oaksford et al., 2005a). In a similar manner, Desmond & MacLachlan (2006) state that a short time elapsed since amputation is correlated with high levels of post trauma distress and symptoms of anxiety - a belief shared also by Oaksford et al. (2005a), according to whom a long time since amputation leads to a more favorable adjustment to limitation. This statement is supported by a study suggesting that depression is marked immediately after amputation and gradually resolves over time (Frank et al., 1984). Phelps et al. (2008) argue that, when high levels of depressive disorders are found in the first two years after amputation (25-35%), they subsequently tend to show a significant decline (mean: 8%).

The passage of time post-amputation causes the user to face negative and positive factors such as: anxiety, depression, anger and guilt, perceived prosthetic mobility, social support, partner support, learning new skills, comorbidity, prosthetic problems, social activity (Asano et al., 2008; Bhojak & Nathawat, 1988; Buffery & Gray, 1972; Burger & Marincek, 1997; C. Murray, 2009).

The factors listed do not necessarily appear universally and the lapse of time necessary for people to re-define their own standard varies from case to case. It is proposed that the presence or absence of a given factor can influence the length of time necessary for a person to move from Phase 1 to Phase 2.

Level of Acceptance of Amputation

The “Level of Acceptance of Amputation” is affected by the degree to which factors occurring during the post-amputation period are dealt with positively or negatively (see previ-

ous point), and, according to our point of view, is positively achieved when cognitive coping strategies are successfully applied. Examples of coping strategies are: 1) engaging an active and confrontational attitude rather than a passive and maladaptive one, 2) being optimistic instead of pessimistic 3) being social and “externally-orientated” instead of cognitive and internally-orientated (Livneh, Antonak, & Gerhardt, 2000) 4) reversing life goals and priorities 5) accommodating traumatic experience and 6) seeking beneficial aspects (Phelps et al., 2008). As mentioned in the section “psychological aspects of prosthetic users”, it is also important to acknowledge the role of “meaning-making” (Taylor, 1983) if a successful post-traumatic growth is to occur after amputation (Dunn, 1996; Oaksford, Frude, & Cuddihy, 2005b).

Senra et al. (2012) illustrate the emotional changes that occur in lower limb amputees prior to obtaining a new self-identity (Figure 3). The process described by the authors is directly relevant to our work as it proposes, within the process of self-identity change following amputation, the role of prostheses and the embodiment of amputation as final factors in obtaining a new self-identity. Additionally, their research shows that a set of psychological changes occurs prior to the identity change (i.e. changes in self-in-the present, self-biography, self-projection in the future or self-identification with the impairment). Our research views these factors as a set of “coping strategies”.

Two stages post-amputation

In relation to time and to the level of acceptance of amputation, the phases of our graph are described as follows:

Phase 1. The amputee is subject to unpleasant psychological feelings (Horgan & MacLachlan, 2004; Price & Fisher, 2007; Shukla et al., 1982; Whyte & Niven, 2001) and is attracted to devices resembling the realistic look of a limb (i.e. cosmetic devices) that remind the subject of the lost leg. We believe that people do not accept that they have an amputated body - or at least have no desire to show it to others - as they have not (yet) fully accepted that their body is “altered”. In agreement with Pereira et al. (1996) and Carrol and Fyfe (2004), our belief is that cosmetic prostheses with human-leg resemblance can be considered important in the process of “restoring the person’s damaged body image”. We claim that at this stage attraction towards realistic-looking devices has to be conceived as a normal phase that needs to be navigated before a full acceptance of the amputated body may be gained. It is to be hoped that this phase will not last long.

Phase 2. The amputee gains a better acceptance of their “mutilated” body, the traumatic experience does not generate increased levels of psychological reaction, and the self-body image is more positive. This belief is supported by the fact that our investigation recorded the presence of a percentage of amputees who were attracted to cosmetic devices, in opposition to a smaller number who were attracted to non-cosmetic devices. Individuals no longer feel like hiding the amputation as they did before, and do not fear using a device with non-human characteristics that clearly “shows” the limb loss. Cairns (2013) recorded that 49/59% of patients rating satisfaction with cosmetic prostheses were neutral or dissatisfied with the color/shape/touch and feel of the devices and stated that

Figure 3 Model for self-identity changes related to lower limb amputation (Senra et al., 2012)

a higher level of realism did not generate further aesthetic attraction. When prosthetic users overcome the normal process of psychological distress and regain confidence they will also be ready to go “beyond” the use of a realistic prosthetic. By wearing a non-cosmetic device they find attractive they will, in return, reach higher levels of confidence in their own bodies.

Our hypothesis is that the attraction towards robotic devices (an attraction that does not exclude a parallel favorable attitude towards cosmetic devices) represents an evolution/improvement in the self-body vision of the amputee. We argue that when amputees “accept” their new body shape they are psychologically more confident and consequently do not see their disability as a visual limitation they need to “hide” using a realistic silicone cosmetic device. The point of view of John (screen-name), a male amputee, is that:

“Although I think that there are lots of reasons you might want a limb that looks lifelike, so many of us acknowledge our loss of a limb and feel that if it is no longer there, why pretend? If it is obviously false, then why not make more of this possible advantage?”

Additionally, we report the words of a male amputee (screen-name: Albert) at an advanced stage of amputation (his amputation having occurred many years ago):

“I have chosen not to hide what I have irreversibly lost. I do not care about this issue (the loss), but it does not occur to me to falsify something that is not reproducible with “silicone”[...]. I could not tolerate the surprise of the people when, as will obviously happen, they discover the deception. No. I prefer to show immediately what has been lost and that it has been replaced by something that does not create feelings of pity but, I hope, aesthetic attraction.”

Albert is not afraid of showing his disability and feels the desire to wear a device that represents aesthetic needs involving a big step beyond the attractions of cosmesis. He is ready to use a prosthesis that does not merely resemble the old limb, or else a device designed to represent an important meaning for the wearer such as “strength”, “speed”, “gracefulness”, “playfulness”. He also hopes the device will generate aesthetic appreciation in external observers as well.

In agreement with this statement, we report the evidence of John:

“I lost my leg – below the knee - when I was 16 [he is currently 45] and until recently I have 'made do' with what was out there, usually something that looked like it had been taken from a shop mannequin. [...] A couple of years back I came across a robotic-looking leg. This style is so appealing that now I shorts in the gym when I'm wearing it. It looks 'cool'! It suggests I am healthy, active, sporty: everything my mannequin leg doesn't!”

In “Design meets Disability” Pullin (2009) argues that prostheses should not merely become replacements of the human limb, as instead their design helps determine and communicate simply what they are. Additionally, he mentions work to apply artistic values to upper limb design, reporting the point of view of the sculptor Jacques Monestier: “I wanted

to transmute what might be considered a disfigurement into something marvelous and exotic. I wanted to create a hand that would no longer cause shame and repulsion. I wanted the amputee to be proud to have it and look at it. And for the people around the amputee, I wanted the prosthetic hand to be an object of healthy curiosity, a work of art”.

Our belief, which matches the points of view reported above, is that the use of a non-cosmetic device may help wearers to see their own bodies as something that is more than an “illusion” of what existed before and is now lost forever. Amputees have the “power” to choose a pleasant looking product design and to show external observers that they are not disabled but, rather, super-abled individuals who are proud of their bodies.

As we mentioned above, attraction and the use of non-cosmetic devices does not imply that all users should deny the use of cosmetic devices for good. We wish only to declare that they should be seen as one option (e.g. for combining with a dress, or for a formal occasion) that can add to the confidence gained by wearing non-cosmetic devices on other occasions. The top fashion model Aimee Mullins, a double amputee, states: “I don't have any issue wearing legs that aren't human-like, but I want the option to have human-looking legs” [“Two legs good, 24 legs better” (Vainshtein, 2012)]. Aimee is the perfect example of a person who has coped well with limb loss and reached a high level of confidence with her body image. We would consider her to be living in Phase 2.

FUTURE WORK

In order to test our hypothesis on the attraction of realism in devices, we have initiated an interview-based experiment based on a revised version of the RGT technique (a method taken from Personal Construct Psychology). The experiment shows the amputee participants a set of non-cosmetic and cosmetic devices and records their level of attraction towards the different levels of realism. The non-cosmetic devices include a set of our own designs that embody a set of principles and elements, as well as meanings (i.e. “stability”, “energy”, “gracefulness”, “lightness” etc.). The aim of the experiment is to compare the level of attraction towards realistic prosthetics among participants with different characteristics such as 1) length of time since amputation 2) gender 3) age 4) personal characteristics / background. Our hope is that the investigation will confirm the arguments advanced in this study.

CONCLUSION

Our belief is that prostheses that are perceived as attractive by prosthetic wearers can improve their body image and psychological well-being. Additionally, the development of acceptance for the new body can influence the attraction felt towards realistic or non-realistic-looking designs. We argue

that prosthetic devices with non-human characteristics can better promote the acceptance of limb loss and provide well-being to the user during a second, post-amputation, phase. Furthermore we argue that cosmetic devices can help wearers to deal with the psychological adjustments associated with limb loss only during the first phase. The hypothesis has been conceived in general terms because, for instance, the length of time needed to arrive at Phase 2 may vary from person to person according to the particular history of each amputee, and there are likely to be many people who might be considered “exceptions”.

This work aims to contribute to academic research on the aesthetics of prosthetic devices and to relate this concept to the promotion of the psychological well-being of prosthetics users. We advance a different perspective regarding the aesthetic needs of amputees, relating this issue to their post-amputation psychological processes. Additionally, we show why the aesthetics of prosthetic devices should receive more attention in the post-amputation rehabilitation process, in order to promote improved self-body image among amputees.

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DESIGN & EMOTION: ATTACHMENT TO SIGNIFICANT OBJECTS AMONG YOUNG PEOPLE

Gabriela Jesumary
Universidade Federal de Pernambuco - Brazil
✉ gabriela.jesumary@gmail.com

Rafael Rattes
Universidade Federal de Pernambuco - Brazil
✉ rafaelrattesaguiar@gmail.com

Tercia Nunes
Universidade Federal de Pernambuco - Brazil
✉ terciav@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This research was conducted in the field of "Design & Emotion" and consisted of identifying evidence relating to levels of attachment to significant objects among a group of young people from the city of Caruaru, Pernambuco State, Brazil. For this purpose, artefacts from two different periods (childhood and the present day) were addressed. Savaş's methodology (Savaş, 2004) was used to categorize the artefacts. Key aspects to help understand the reasons for attachment and the user: object relationship were identified. It was found that present-day artefacts were of most significance, experience of Use, Utility Function and Form being the principal explanations of attachment relationships among the young people interviewed.

KEYWORDS: *Design, Emotion, Affective Bond, Attachment and Product Affectivity.*

INTRODUCTION

The arrival of the new technologies and industrial processes that characterize the present led to a change in the functionalist paradigm in design. The culture of mass production that predominated at the start of the industrialization process gave way to flexible production techniques that sought to respond to the individuality of the user. In recent years functionality has become implicit in the act of designing, and important new aspects of the design process such as emotional, cultural and social factors have become increasingly necessary and important. Consequently, the user has become the focus of the design process and user needs and aspirations have taken center stage.

In this scenario, other changes have also occurred, especially in the relations between individuals and artefacts. This relationship has become a topic of interest for many researchers in various disciplines, including design, neuroscience, psychology and anthropology. Therefore, it is of utmost importance to understand, first, the individual and then groups of users, in order to address the needs and desires of the latter through the design of artefacts.

Despite the different names that have been given to this relationship in the field of design – for example, Design & Emo-

tion and Experiential Design - the object of study does not change: the emotional competence of products to provide positive user experiences. This approach does not undermine the principle of functionality but refers to the belief that designers should always take emotion into account during the design process. In theory this increases the period of time artefacts remain in the possession of consumers, making it possible to reduce the numbers of products that need to be purchased. However, never in history have human beings possessed so many objects, though their symbolic value is less and less noticed, leading to empty and superficial relationships (Cardoso, 2012).

This phenomenon is due, in part, to what the authors call the ephemerality of the product. Every day, companies release new versions of products, resulting in the creation of new needs, in a process Sudjic has described as a "serial seduction" (Sudjic, 2010). And yet, these artefacts lack durability and cannot resist the continued use they are put to: they are soon replaced by more modern versions. Thus, as a consequence of the short period of contact between user and product, little or no affective attachment develops between them. In contrast, the use of emotional factors in the production of objects leads to growing consumption, creating a significant volume of waste that conflicts with another yearning of the modern consumer: sustainability.

Designers can contribute to solving this problem by recourse to their knowledge of other areas related to emotions, feelings, affection, culture, consumption, etc., seeking solutions that help to design products that are consistent with current realities. This is not a solution to all problems, but a step towards discovering and understanding the motivations behind individual choices.

The current research was conducted in 2012 in the city of Caruaru, Pernambuco State, Brazil. It focuses on understanding the affective bond between young people and objects that were significant to them in their childhoods and/or in the present. Respondents were students in the first semester of the Design course at the Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, Centro Acadêmico do Agreste.

PRODUCT AFFECTIVITY

In the past, the practical function and utility of the product were key elements for the development of new artefacts. Nowadays, issues such as the meanings assigned by the sensations, perceptions and emotions that objects transmit must be included in new projects.

The current situation points to a need to project beyond the utilitarian sense of a product, so that the user may assign special personal meanings that result from their positive experiences with it. Thus, the meanings attributed to objects are reflected in ideas, values, past experiences, living conditions and future expectations. That is, the meanings given to products as a result of their use arises as a consequence of the relationship between the human being and the object. An artefact that individuals experience as merely functional does not generate any special, emotional, bond (Schifferstein et al, 2004; Cardoso, 2012; Mugge, 2008).

Thus, the affectivity of the product may be defined, according Schifferstein, Mugge & Hekkert (2004), as the strength of the emotional bond that individuals experience as a result of their relationship with a particular object. Emotions can cause either attachment or detachment, depending on the affective reaction the artefact evokes. Savaş (2004, p. 318) defines attachment as "a positive emotional state of the relationship between an individual and a product, which indicates a strong linkage between them." The result of this relationship is that people consider the product to be a part of themselves, and therefore have a strong desire to keep it.

Michael Lacroix argues that the theme of *emotion* is central to these relationships, but the idea that there is an "awakening to affectivity" should be viewed with caution. The author argues that the craving for strong sensations, however ephemeral, is accompanied by an anesthetizing of sensitivity. "We feel lots of emotions, but we don't know how to feel" (Lacroix, 2006, p.11, authors' translation). This happens because modern humans are looking for explosive, instant, experiences of excitement, marked by strong sensations. This phenomenon

is also clearly present in the field of advertising. For example, designers seek to make products that excite the emotions on the understanding that "emotion sells". Lacroix explains that there are two sides to this: "First, [it] shows that a return to emotion is taking place. (...) Second, they warn us, even because of their role in the consumer society, the danger of misuse of emotion" (Lacroix, 2006, p.18, authors' translation). This argument constitutes an effective questioning of emotions, whose consequences may be different from what was originally intended.

Therefore, the building of a strong and positive affective bond between users and products is considered to be a design strategy that might help delay the rapid disposal of a product or its replacement with new versions. This is because individuals tend to keep those products that adequately meet all their needs and which - whether for utilitarian or emotional reasons - promote special meanings for them (Schifferstein et al, 2004; Mugge, 2008; Savaş, 2004).

Savaş (2004, p.318) defines detachment as a "a negative emotional state of the relationship between an individual and a product which indicates the lack of linkage between them", arguing that even if the product works as expected this does not necessarily create a special emotional bond with the user, making its disposal or replacement easier (Mugge, 2008).

Modern humans live, then, in a state of constant emotional stimulus and permanent agitation but are, at the same time, unable to experience authentic feelings. Lacroix (2006, p. 161) affirms that "the cult of emotion can be the best or the worst of things and, often, what we see today is the spectacle of the worst". He concludes that a solution would be to replace the shock-emotions (rapid and short-lived) with contemplation-emotions (linked to memory - durable and more likely to be converted into a sense). This process would imply a need for quality of subject and object (Lacroix, 2006).

It is understandable that individuals may feel attached to people, objects, brands, etc. For products, this attachment occurs at different levels of abstraction, varying according to their nature (Mugge, 2008). Mugge further argues that attachment varies between Specific Products - where the user has an emotional bond with a particular object that does not dissolve if the original object is replaced by an identical one, because of the uniqueness of the context in which the original was purchased or used. A similar phenomenon occurs with so-called General Products, referring to a type of product where others of the same genre, which need not necessarily be physically identical, can be easily replaced.

These issues have a direct influence on the relationship between the product and the individual, and especially the responsibility of the design professional to respond to them. For this, Lacroix (2006, p. 162) suggests, "(...) we must ensure the quality of the objects to which we give our attention. These objects should be elevated, noble, worthy of admiration, without which the contemplative attention we assign them is in unstable equilibrium."

Design and Emotion

In Brazil and in the rest of the world many researchers have argued that the study of emotions and emotional relationships, reactions and responses that characterize the connection between user and product are fundamental to the design process. Thus, Hekkert & McDonagh (2003) argue that emotional responses should be considered at the point when the design goals are set, and not just as a side effect of the main function of the product. The authors add that these emotional reactions are not only derived from the relationship of the user with the product, but the context in which it occurs. This interaction is of great importance to the final experience.

In general, the objective of the Design & Emotion approach is to analyze emotional responses to products and to develop tools and methods that aid in the creation of relationships between products and users (Overbeeke & Hekkert, 1999; Kurtgözü, 2003). Apparently, though, there is no consensus concerning the nomenclature employed. Most authors use terms such as Design & Emotion, though variations exist, such as Emotional Design (Norman, 2004); Pleasure-based Design (Jordan, 2002) and Experience Design (Jääskö et al. 2003). In Brazil, names like *Design Experiencial* (Buccini, 2006), *Design & Emoção* (Damázio, 2006) *Design Emocional* (Iida & Muhlenberg, 2006) have been used.

This paper adopts the term "Design & Emotion", which has been proposed as a field of research in design by the Design & Emotion Society and was presented at the First International Conference on Design & Emotion.

It is well known that there is a proliferation of objects in everyday life that may be considered to form links between people, and act as mediators of actions in life, evoking all sorts of emotions and feelings (Damázio et al., 2008). According to Norman (2004), objects have personal components, which neither designers nor manufacturers can provide, but that exist because of their powers of motivation and meaning. Thus, the meanings of the symbolic function of a product are assigned by users according to an intangible process of personal interpretation (Desmet et al. 2001). Therefore, emotionally relevant objects may be present in memory, as a result of the recovery of the details of the relationship between the user and the product.

The artefacts of memory have been studied by many researchers, including Vera Damázio (2006) and Cristiane Menezes (2007). These authors propose that such artefacts may be considered successful, in as much as they produce a positive relationship between the user and the product, leading to a lasting relationship. The importance of studies that are designed better to understand human emotions and their capabilities and limitations is, then, clear. In the field of design things could not be otherwise, since products are in constant interaction with their human users, and research of this kind will result in more sophisticated products, contributing to a more sustainable future.

PROCEDURE

The paper is based on work submitted as a supplementary requirement for the degree of Bachelor of Design at the Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, Centro Acadêmico do Agreste. Its aim is to collect and analyze data in order to improve understanding of the affective bond between people and objects that were significant for them either in childhood and/or in the present day.

Because the research is preliminary and exploratory, and not a representative study – though it is based on a significant amount of data – it was necessary to choose a sample to which the instruments of data collection could be applied using semi-structured interviews.

The study was carried out in Caruaru, in the arid zone of Pernambuco, Brazil. The sample was chosen to respond to a series of research questions. Which aspects of objects generate good or bad feelings about them? Are changes in technology and communications key to this emotional bond? Do certain factors that cause good and bad emotions remain independent of technological progress? Are these factors, or some aspects of them, un-bounded by time?

In the light of these questions it was decided to focus the research on first semester students of the Design course at the Universidade Federal de Pernambuco. The sample was made up of randomly selected students enrolled in the first year; and the interviews were conducted during the first weeks of term, thus preventing the answers being influenced by the respondents having received some academic orientation. The final sample was made up of seven young women and two young men, totaling nine respondents, whose ages ranged between 17 and 23.

A second stage of data collection occurred with the application of a semi-structured interview, which explored the issues further. All interviews were duly recorded using a digital camera. The interview was divided into two phases:

- Memories of objects that had a special place in the affective memory of respondents when they were children, particularly those they liked. The same information was gathered for objects respondents currently possessed;
- An introspective exercise to recall sensations, affective memories and aesthetic perceptions about the objects mentioned, in order to gather details of the sensations that provoked respondent views of the objects and made them special.

After the data had been collected, it had to be classified and analyzed. This was done using the methodology proposed by Savaş (2004), for the characterization of data.

According to Savaş it is possible to identify both the *Nature* of the attributes of objects that are related to attachment and detachment and the *Reasons* they function as they do. However, due to the extensive amount of data obtained during the research, in this paper, it is only possible to present a snippet of information provided in the interviews, explaining why

consumers felt attachment. These reasons are divided into 6 groups of attachment: the Past, Experience, Utilitarian Function, Personal Identity, Social Identity and Form.

ANALYSIS

The nine respondents cited 53 products as having produced an attachment relationship in childhood, alongside 44 present-day products that provoke attachment today.

The Past

With this group it is understood that the relationship involves existing lived experiences and memories. The group subdivided into three sub-groups described below. 56.6% of childhood items mentioned had something to do with the past, while for present-day objects the percentage was 46.6%. These results indicate that for childhood objects the past plays a more important role than for present-day objects, since these items are generally obtained as gifts and refer to a person or place.

The sub-groups for this group are as follows:

Family Heirloom: corresponding to gifts from family members. 32.1% of childhood objects were reported as family gifts, while for present-day objects the percentage was 22.2%. This phenomenon presents itself spontaneously. It was observed that respondents tended to explain who they had obtained their special product from, for example:

"It was my uncle who gave it to me, and he died not long after." (Interviewee 5: about a cloth ball)

Memory: related to those objects that resemble a particular person or time. According to the data obtained, this is the biggest reason for items the group, accounting for 41.4% of childhood items, while the total for present-day objects was 42.2%. It was noticed that many of the products have a strong attachment relationship associated with memory, as in the following response:

- "I liked it because my aunt gave it to me the first time I went to her house." (Interviewee 6: about a Patamon doll)

Habitual Ownership: corresponding to those products which respondents have owned or used for a long period of time. The sub-group applied to 15.1% of childhood objects and 26.6% of present-day ones. This can be explained because most respondents had developed a long-term relationship with objects during childhood despite the fact their contact with the object had been fleeting, as explained in the following testimony:

"I got this this shirt when I was tiny: I think my mom gave it to me when I was a baby." (Interviewee 5: about a white shirt)

Experience

Experience consists in the relationship between respondents and the object, i.e., the experience they have when using the

product. Experience may be divided into three sub-groups, described below. 73.6% of childhood artefacts were classified as belonging to this group, compared to 68.9% of present-day objects. In both cases, this was the attribute that most stood out, leading to the conclusion that the sensations arising from this relationship are fundamental for the attachment to objects.

The sub-groups for this group are as follows:

Enjoyment: corresponding to objects that provide pleasure in their use. This was the most important reason, which in childhood objects was obtained by 49% of reported items, a figure that reached 48.9% for present-day objects. When an individual purchases an object they expect it to fulfill its practical function and to provide pleasure in its use. Enjoyment is thus central to the affective relationship, as may be seen from the following testimony:

- "It is interesting that today I feel naked without a cell phone, I feel kind of lost, you know? It is as though my phone were part of me. I have everything I need on it: internet, cell phone, camera, music, games, calendar, etc." (Interviewee 9: on their phone).

Frequent Actions: objects used frequently in daily activities. The respondents reported that 13.2% of childhood items belonged to this sub-group, compared to 42.2% for present-day objects. This large difference is explained by the fact that the need for objects evolves as the individual gets older, as may be seen from the following testimony

- "I mean, everywhere I went, at school, at home, I always took it with me. Like, it was a toy that, if I'm going out, I'll take it" (Interviewee 5: about a cloth ball).

Desirable Feelings: consists of the feelings evoked by the experience of using objects. Respondents tended to explain the feelings that the products generated in various ways. The incidence for childhood items was 45.3% compared to 40% for present-day objects. This is illustrated by the following response:

- "They give me a sense of security: when I use them I feel more capable and less blind." (Interviewee 9: about their glasses)

Utilitarian Function

This group reflects the basic utility of the product and its performance. As with the previous attributes, the group is also divided into three sub-groups, described below. It was observed that for childhood objects, only 5.66% of the items were so classified compared to 48.9% of present-day products. These contrasting figures show that Utilitarian Function plays a key role in attachment to current objects, since use becomes more important, and even essential, over time.

The sub-groups for this group are as follows:

Utility is associated with the needs of users. This attribute was present for 5.66% of childhood objects and 46.6% of present-day ones, demonstrating that in childhood the utility of the product is probably not a reason for attachment. This is illustrated by the following testimony on a present-day item:

"I like it because it is really necessary. I live on the run. My watch helps me with the notion of time... it also brings me security" (Interviewee 2: about his watch).

Performance concerns the ability of artefacts to fulfill their basic function correctly. The respondents did not associate any object from childhood with this attribute compared to 26.6% of present-day products. This data is related to the fact that as they get older young people begin to purchase products that are useful to them and that performance and quality of these products is key to attachment:

"My cell is normal, not big and not small. Its touch screen is quite simple. But it has a wonderful camera!" (Interviewee 2: about their phone)

Tools of Trade are those artefacts that are used for work or to make money. Again, no childhood object was included in this sub-group, against 4.44% for present-day objects. However, as in childhood, present-day objects had little significance, probably because they are still young, or there is no present need. The reason for this is that few children work or engage in activities that have assumed importance in their daily lives:

"Initially it was out of necessity, then I started to like it because, with it, I can do everything associated with photos and it is useful beyond all the projects that I create using it - beyond the limits of the imagination, beyond the interactivity produced through internet." (Interviewee 3: about a computer)

Personal Identity

Personal Identity involves the individual satisfaction provided by a product, to the point that it reflects the identity and lifestyle of an individual. The sub-groups are described below. It was found that for respondents, 52.8% of childhood objects were classified in this group against 40% of present-day items.

The sub-groups for this group are as follows:

Reflection of Self refers to those products that reflect the user's identity and suit their lifestyles. This property corresponds to 37.7% of childhood items, and only 15.5% of present-day objects. This result shows that during childhood the respondents' need for self-reflection, or to belong to a group is more significant than that at present. It is believed this relates to the process of self-discovery:

- "I like the Barbie because it was a character that marked my childhood and still marks me today. When I was a kid wanted to look like her... I grew up, dyed my hair blonde, I've always liked pink. The Barbie was kind of a DIVA to me (...) I think that because of my introduction to Barbie you can understand why I love this bag right?" (Interviewee 2: on a Barbie purse)

Symbolization of Values involves objects that become personal symbols and to the personification of artefacts. 26.4% of artefactchildhood artefacts fell into this sub-group, and 22.6% of present-day objects. This relationship is described in the following testimony:

- "It was my favorite precisely because the other Barbies are usually all similar. It's all pink dress and stuff but this one was

different: she was rural and not that fashionable Barbie. Her hair was dark. My Barbies were all blondes, and I liked her because she was different". (Interviewee 3: about Barbie Cowboy).

Self-made: those products that have been constructed by the individual. Only 1.9% of childhood objects fell under this sub-group and no present-day items. Thus, for this group of respondents this sub-group had little relevance for attachment. One respondent described the attachment to their handmade customized object as follows:

- "They were just the color of clay and I had the habit of painting them. I used to paint them in my own way. I liked to be able to buy them undecorated and then paint them" (Interviewee 3: about small clay pots).

The sub-group **Interests and Goals** included artefacts that helped respondents pursue their personal interests or achieve some goal. No childhood items were included in this sub-group, against 4.44% of present-day objects. This shows that for this generation, such artefacts are not significant for attachment.

- "I like the camera because, through photography, I can describe and mark important moments for me and others. It is more a more loving relationship than professional, but all this love for photography is related to my adventures." (Interviewee 3: on their camera)

Social Identity

Social Identity: this sub-group involves the adaptation of objects to reflect the individual within their social environment. The four sub-groups were are described below. 41.5% of childhood objects were included in this sub-group compared to 22.2% of present-day objects.

The sub-groups for this group are as follows:

Social Status: corresponds to product quality according to the social aspirations of respondents. 11.3% of childhood objects were included in the sub-group, and only of 4.44% of present-day items. The data indicate that during childhood the need to belong to or appear to be part of a particular group was more important in terms of attachment than is the case today:

"I had three brothers and an older sister, but my older sister was always the "big girl", so because I was younger I played with my brothers. So I loved boys' toys which were the pinnacle for me, because I wanted to associate myself with them; I always wanted to be surrounded by them, which couldn't happen if I was playing with dolls" (Interviewee 5: On a toy car)

Image: the way a person is seen as a result of the use they make of an artefact. 24.5% of childhood objects were included in this sub-group compared to 8.69% of present-day objects:

"When I arrived there with the most colorful marbles and everyone wanted to play with me to win them from me, but I was good at marbles. So I thought it was very good" (Interviewee 5: on marbles).

Union consists of those products that deliver an experience together with other people, such as friends or family. 20.6% of childhood products were classified in this sub-group, against only 11.1% of present-day objects. Thus, for the respondents, use and user experiences were more important in childhood than today.

"Actually I almost failed my third year because of them ... But I couldn't help reading. They were the basis of many conversations I had with my best friend, Tassio. We competed to see who could read the books fastest. What made me like them very much was the bond of friendship they helped make.... These books are awesome.... I recommend reading them with a friend!" (Interviewee 6: About the Percy Jackson books)

Opinion of Others: artefacts that are desired and appreciated by others. 13.2% of childhood artefacts were categorized within this sub-group compared to 11.1% of present-day objects. Thus, in both periods the opinion of others is important for the relationship between individuals and objects:

"But I had no reason not to take it off. At first I only wore it when I went out. Then one day my friend saw me using it and liked it a lot, and from then on I never took it off, well only on a few rare occasions" (Interviewee 7: describing a pendant on a cord).

Form

Form corresponds to the physical elements of a product. Respondents tend to describe the size, colors, shapes, style, etc of objects. For 73.6% of childhood items respondents noted that the aesthetics of artefacts was essential for attachment. 48.9% of present-day products were included in this sub-group - the second highest reason for attachment. Therefore, it is understood that form and aesthetics are key to the attachment, as may be observed in the following testimony:

"My phone. I liked its geometric shapes and its color (also black), I especially liked the fact it was uniform in its thickness and it was completely flat. It wasn't very good, but I loved 'those curves'" (Interviewee 6: on their old cell phone).

CONCLUSIONS

When investigating the affective relations between individuals and products it is possible to identify numerous clues that enable important aspects in the bond of attachment to be understood. This is clear from the analyses of the interviews and questionnaires conducted with the respondent group of young people from the city of Caruaru, Pernambuco State, Brazil. Since this is a qualitative research study, it is possible to identify a strong trend among designers to contribute to projects focused on emotion and feeling. However, it is important to recognize that, as the research involved a small sample in a specific region, it is not possible to generalize the results.

From the results obtained, it was possible to identify numerous attributes relevant to understanding the affective bond between person and object. These features not only help strengthen the relationship between individuals and objects also have a favorable impact on environmental issues. Thus, to the point that users experience an increased emotional bond with the objects they use they tend to keep them for longer. This results in a decrease in the accumulation of garbage and the frequency with which artefacts are quickly discarded as a result of their ephemerality.

In consequence it was possible to identify and categorize Reasons why attachment occurs. Among the most important reasons cited by young people were: Experience, Utilitarian Function and Form, which were most significant for present-day objects. The data illustrate significant differences that point to potentially very distinct patterns. Changes over time, and technological advances, may be crucial in explaining this change. However, some aspects that promote the affective bond are timeless, such as aesthetic considerations (shape, color, etc.), which are important factors to the relationship, as individuals tend to feel attracted to objects that they find beautiful. It was also observed that for young people who are no longer children the experiences of using an object are considered important for the construction of attachment

As has been seen, there are countless possibilities for research aimed at strengthening the emotional bond between people and objects. The focus on such studies is recent, especially in Brazil, where there is still little academic research carried out from this perspective. Therefore, it is both necessary and important to carry out further, more detailed, studies in the field, in order to improve our understanding of the reasons for attachment and to contribute to the important task of strengthening the emotional bond between individuals and objects.

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WILL – WELLBEING INITIATIVE FOR LEARNING AND LIVING

HOW CAN STRATEGIC DESIGN HELP CHRONIC DISEASE PATIENTS MANAGE THEIR HEALTH AND WELLBEING?

Marian Ana Barrera, Carolina Rivera, Nazli Ceren Binyildirim, Hussain Indorewala, David-Georges Renaud, Denise C. Tahara
 a-e Masters in Design Management Program, Pratt Institute
 fNew York Medical College School of Health Sciences and Practice
 ✉ abarrera.ma@gmail.com, bcarorivera84@gmail.com, cncbinyildirim@gmail.com, dhussainsindorewala@gmail.com, edavidg.renaud@gmail.com, fdenise_tahara@nymc.edu

ABSTRACT

Chronic diseases are considered the epidemic of the 21st century. Present healthcare systems are weak in coordination and communication to address chronic conditions since they were not designed for such purpose. Chronic diseases are difficult to manage, making daily life a challenge for patients. With the purpose of addressing “How strategic design can help chronic disease patients manage their health and wellbeing,” WILL (Wellbeing Initiative for Learning & Living) designed a model using strategic design, design thinking and Triple Bottom Line by Design plus Culture (TBLD+C) framework. Strategic design contributes to the application of traditional design principles to create more resilient and durable solutions, design thinking adds the human-centered approach and TBLD+C provide a combined understanding of People-Planet-Profit accompanied by Culture. The intent was to design a patient-centered innovation that engages all stakeholders and empowers patients to manage their diseases. Overall, WILL aims to develop a strategic care management system to propel a movement in health and wellbeing industries towards improving patients’ quality of life.

KEYWORDS: *Chronic Disease Management | Wellbeing and Quality of Life | Strategic Design | Design Thinking*

INTRODUCTION

“The growing number of persons suffering from major chronic illnesses face many obstacles in coping with their condition, not least of which is medical care that often does not meet their needs for effective clinical management, psychological support, and information” (Wagner, et al, 2001, pg. 1). Chronic diseases (Non Communicable Diseases or NCDs) progress slowly and may last indefinitely while limiting productivity, independence and decreasing quality of life in the process (Institute of Medicine, 2012). Thus, the patients’ lives change irreversibly with their changing medical conditions.

Different models of care have been designed revealing the need for a multidisciplinary approach to treating NCDs. These models are based on the general principle that the patient’s involvement and ability to manage the condition is indispensable for the overall success of the treatment. Still, these models have not been planned to be adaptable to different environmental settings (e.g. patient’s access to healthy foods, usual source of care, and to technology).

WILL is a strategic design program whose purpose is to drive social innovation by adapting healthcare services to optimize resources within communities. In the case of NCDs, WILL proposes a model formulated from the basis of design and strategic thinking. This model is intended to be adaptable for the community involved, taking into account available resources, access to technology, and the specific characteristics of the disease.

CHRONIC DISEASE OVERVIEW

NCDs are long-lasting conditions that may be controlled but not cured and affect the population worldwide (Center for Managing Chronic Disease, n.d.). Heart disease, cancer, diabetes and autoimmune conditions are examples of NCDs that account for a substantial health burden globally (World Health Organization, 2005a).

Ironically, NCDs are among the most common and high-cost health conditions, but they are also among the most prevent-

able, and a majority of them can be effectively controlled (Center for Managing Chronic Disease, n.d.). NCDs have great impact due to: unfavorable effects on quality of life, causing premature death, and causing high, underappreciated economic burden for individuals, families, and communities (World Health Organization, 2005b).

NCDs cause recurrent disability at different levels often for decades or long periods. The most common measurement used to calculate this burden is the Disability Adjusted Life Years (DALYs). DALYs are a combination of years lost due to premature death and time spent in less than full health. Around 86% of DALYs correspond to people under the age of 70 with approximately 16 million deaths per year of people in this age group (World Health Organization, 2005b).

Furthermore, the economic liability that NCDs represent is unsustainable. In the US, NCDs contribute 75% of the \$2 trillion invested in annual healthcare (Institute of Medicine, 2012). Adding the economic implications of premature death, DALYs, and expenses for health care, treatment and secondary consequences of the illness; NCDs consequently pose a major concern for overall community productivity.

CURRENT SITUATION

Although genetics and aging influence the predisposition of individuals to NCDs, environmental factors, extending from pollutant exposure, to lower socioeconomic circumstances (e.g., poor diet or lack of access to healthcare services) have a considerable and unavoidable impact on the incidence and development of NCDs (Sears & Genuis, 2012).

General treatment and research on NCDs has mostly failed at understanding the big picture with a systematic approach to these conditions, many of which can be associated with unhealthy diet, stress, lack of physical activity, improper housing, daily exposure to toxins, etc. given that such circumstances are mostly related to low socioeconomic status, NCDs tend to be more problematic for low-income families (World Health Organization, 2005a; Sears & Genuis, 2012). Moreover, there are clear gaps in the general treatment for NCDs such as patients' understanding of the condition and management plan, lack of proper lifestyle and environmental conditions analysis, and deficiencies in multidisciplinary approaches (Harris & Zwar, 2007).

Care for NCD patients is not well organized because worldwide systems are not designed for these types of diseases. This results in overuse or underuse of services, unnecessary medical payments, and confusion due to opposite/conflicting advice from health care providers. Globally, healthcare systems need to undergo reforms to reshape the service for chronic care. The change should include training and education of care providers, communication protocols, support systems, and awareness campaigns among others (Anderson, 2010).

WINDOW OF OPPORTUNITY

The World Health Organization (2008) has defined prevention and control of NCDs as "Tackling the world's biggest killers and addressing key challenges to global development in the 21st century" (p. 5). Wagner, et al. (2001) rightfully stated, "High-quality NCD care is characterized by productive interactions between practice team and patients" (p. 68). Facilitating communication by providing opportunities for feedback from the patient, enabling the improved flow of messages between provider and patient, and supporting patients' self-management, is productive and effective when all actors are actively involved, informed, and prepared. Patients should be ready to take advantage of the treatment and guidance they receive to be engaged in improving their health and wellbeing (Wagner, Austin, et al., 2001).

There is a worldwide shortage of healthcare resources, specifically primary care providers and a supporting healthcare team, which limits access to primary health care. A coordinated and collaborative healthcare team is needed to supplement provision of the ongoing services needed by patients with NCDs.

The real challenge is how to combine and utilize the resources available and improve communication and information flow that can enable patients and doctors to be on the same page. Tools, resources and means developed around the actors should facilitate this process.

The constraints in the current system present a design opportunity. Since people suffering from NCDs will live with their condition throughout their entire lives, the goal of treatment and health services should focus on quality of life. By addressing pain management, continuous informed medical treatments, adjustment to the social and psychological burden, and use and accessibility of community resources, NCD patients will have a better quality of life and be better prepared to manage their conditions; enhancing productivity, independence and promoting collaborative management at the same time.

WHAT HAS BEEN DONE?

Different healthcare models have been designed to address NCD treatment. Most of them are developed with the purpose of empowering patients to self-manage their condition properly and leave the healthcare team as supporting actors. Several of these care management models are described below.

The Chronic Care Model (CCM) was developed for healthcare organizations as a guide to improve chronic care, especially for low-income populations (Wagner, et al., 2001). This model considers healthcare organizations, community resources, self-management support, delivery system design, decision support and clinical information systems with the intent to reinforce the patients' and their families' role in managing NCDs, help the patient set goals, identify barriers and plan

how to overcome the barriers in order to achieve the goals (Wagner, et al., 2001).

The Stepped Care Model presents a framework for professional support that is based on patients' responses to treatment (Von Korff & Tiemens, 2000), recognizing that all patients have different conditions and may require different levels of care. The purpose is to build a partnership with common goals and a care plan followed by active follow-up. As the patients move up each of the four levels, the collaborative management gets stronger, as it becomes more of a 'team task' (Von Korff & Tiemens, 2000).

Flinders Model allows doctors to develop collaborative care plans with their clients and to assess patients' self-management capabilities. They use "A number of standardized tools/forms: the Partners in Health Scale, Cue and Response Questionnaire, Problem and Goals, and Care Plan" (Victorian State Government, n.d., pg. 2).

To provide a basic protocol of how clinical teams should properly tend to chronic disease patients, the World Health Organization designed a five-step model (5As) with recommendations and tips to improve general treatment: Assess, Advise, Agree, Assist, Arrange. This model considers different variables that health providers should implement in order to establish suitable processes to treat NCD patients. For example, the use of neutral, common language when discussing diseases and treatments, assessing patient's goals, knowledge and beliefs before implementing a plan of action, and assisting with information, tools and follow ups.

All of these models were designed to include the patient in the management of their NCDs and a collaborative and coordinated healthcare team. However, they do not provide ongoing opportunities for the patient to provide feedback about what is working, and what is not working, including the challenges they face in their built and living environments to adhere to their care plans. Without this vital information, the provider cannot make adjustments to the care plan such as including nurse practitioners, physical therapists, nutritionists or other allied health professionals on the disease management team or provide alternative protocols to improve the patients' quality of life.

According to an initiative from the Victorian State Government (n.d.), "The best model is the one that meets the person's needs for self-management support; this will vary between people and at different times for any one individual" (pg. 3). The challenge relies on succeeding in designing the right intellectual and behavioral toolkit to produce an impact on the health and wellbeing industries since the existing models have not proven to be efficient enough when implemented in isolation (Australian Government Department of Health, n.d.). Different factors in the specific context must be considered to fully tackle the patient's needs. Adaptability and flexibility for a model to be implemented regardless the type of disease, the technological ability of patients, caregivers, and healthcare team, and the environmental settings surrounding implementation, are essential for the proper delivery of chronic disease care.

METHODOLOGY

Based on our literature review, we developed a model that addresses the gaps identified in the current models. We designed our model using strategic design, design thinking and the Triple Bottom Line by Design plus Culture (TBLD+C) framework. Strategic design contributes to the application of traditional design principles to create more resilient and durable solutions; design thinking adds the human-centered approach and TBLD+C provides a combined understanding of People-Planet-Profit accompanied by Culture. Our model is based on a strategic design system (Figure 1) intended to address chronic disease management. The patient is at the core and is directly influenced by his/her context, which includes his/her social core, healthcare team, the community, and the environment. Factors such as communication, education, feedback, and collaboration also impact the patient's health and wellbeing.

To formalize our model, we designed and conducted a survey of a broad sample of patients, providers and caregivers to identify the flow of information, gaps and barriers in the communication processes, contributions and influence of each actor, and opportunities and insights that should be part of the model being designed.

The questions were designed to gather information related to medication systems, socio-economic status, lifestyle (diet and exercise), appointments and follow-ups, and other general information relevant to improving the management of NCDs, as well as demographic and lifestyle information. The purpose was to better understand provider resources, the en-

Strategic Design System

Guidelines and principles for the design proposal

Adapted from Pediatric Patient-Centered Framework, 2014, Tahara & Laufer

Figure 1. Strategic Design System

Country	# of Patients (N=197)	# of Doctors (N=53)	# of Caregivers (N=173)
India	109	5	115
Colombia	53	26	21
Turkey	35	22	37

Figure 2. Response Chart

environment in which the patients live, as well as personal factors (age, type of disease, economic status, etc.) and lifestyle factors (behaviors, environment, nutrition, exercise, etc.). All the information gathered enabled the research team to identify challenges, barriers, and breaches in the implementation of and adherence to care plans and opportunities to improve NCD management.

The surveys were translated into three different languages: Spanish, Turkish, and Marathi and were administered in Colombia, Turkey and India. These locations were selected for convenience reasons since members of the research team had access to healthcare facilities in the designated location and posed an opportunity to gather valuable information about how NCD management is addressed within different cultures including socio-economic differences.

Cross-cultural results revealed the un-tackled opportunity posed by engaging caregivers as key participants in patients' NCD management. For example in India, since many caregivers share the same household with patients, they have major involvement in their day-to-day activities, including those related to health and wellbeing.

Data also showed that different resources and access to technology confirm the need to have an adaptable and inclusive intervention model rather than a specific tool with exclusive requirements that targets a population with specific characteristics.

Lastly, providers manifested a concern regarding resources and means available to enhance communication due to time and human capital constraints. Additionally, results suggested that socio-economic status is related to healthcare literacy and it could be perceived that people with more financial resources among the survey participants, probably had better education compared to others. As a result, they have a better understanding of how to manage their condition and have a clear idea of how to approach communication with providers asking questions and researching their conditions. As this was a pilot study and used convenience sampling, more data will need to be gathered and analyzed to inform our design solution.

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STORYTELLING AS A METHOD OF GATHERING PERCEPTIONS AND EXPERIENCES IN HUMAN-CENTERED DESIGN

THE RELATION BETWEEN CHILDREN AND THEIR EYEGLASSES

Iana Garófalo Chaves

The Faculty of Architecture and Urbanism, University of São Paulo – FAUUSP – Brazil

✉ iana@usp.br / iana_chaves@hotmail.com

Agnacilda Silva Rocha

Centro Paula Souza – São Paulo- Brazil

✉ rochaas.d@gmail.com

Cibele Haddad Taralli

The Faculty of Architecture and Urbanism, University of São Paulo – FAUUSP - Brazil

✉ cibelet@usp.br / cibeletaralli@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Given that eyeglasses are specialized orthotic products, we can affirm that their designers contribute to human needs. Among those who wear eyeglass, children require special attention.

The study presented in this article is part of a research that aims to define guidelines for the design of children's eyeglasses. A Human-Centered Design methodology was used for this research, including a Storytelling method to consider the relevant aspects of the product for potential and central users.

This article presents the data collected using this method applied to thirty children. The stories were analyzed, and categories were defined in which it was possible to evaluate emotional, formal, medical, reflexive and functional subjects mentioned by the children. The results and discussion will provide specific and more subjective content that will be combined with other methods to be part of the final design guidelines for children's eyeglasses.

KEYWORDS: *Human-Centered Design, Eyeglasses Design, Storytelling, Product Experience, User Centered Design.*

INTRODUCTION

Eyeglasses are specialized orthotic products, essential for many people's daily existence. As such their designers contribute to human needs.

Currently, eyeglasses are known for their formal aspect and their main corrective functions. However, some argue that the product is has become more of an accessory than a utility, as stated by Bastian (2001, p.35) "Designed for production in large scale, the eyeglasses are objects of industrial design with the refinement of handcrafted pieces...which puts them between design and fashion."

However, beyond aspects of consumption and fashion, eyeglasses should be primarily conceived and designed for those who wear them, as they are personal and fundamental aids to everyday life, and an extension of the body and the human senses. Therefore, the product should be developed considering guidelines that focus on the physical and emotional needs of its wearers.

Among the wearers, children's eyeglasses demand studies and extensive research, as reported by Gozlan (2007, p.52) "the guidance needed for eyeglasses for children is one of the toughest in the daily routine of the optical field, because it requires technical skills and also psychological competence for adapting the child and guiding parents".

Therefore, the design of children's eyeglasses must consider, in addition to formal and aesthetic requirements (ergonomics, anthropometry, performance and usability), perceptual, subjective and emotional aspects that stimulate children's affections for them, making them pleasurable and attractive to use.

The complete research adopts the perspective of Human-Centered Design (HCD), which concerns the way in which people see, interpret and live with some artifact, also considering the meaning as central part of its discourse (Krippendorff, 2000). The author also comments that the application of HCD must be performed in a defined group of stakeholders. For this study, the following stakeholders were established: children who wear eyeglasses; their guardians; the optical attendants; pediatric ophthalmologists and factories/designers of eyeglasses.

The goal of the complete research is to define guidelines for the design of children's eyeglasses. To achieve this goal, different methods will be applied for each one of the stakeholders mentioned before. This paper presents a part of the research and the results of the Storytelling method applied with one of the stakeholder groups: children who wear eyeglasses.

METHOD

Storytelling is considered a narrative tool that is currently used in various fields of knowledge, from pedagogy to marketing, and it is also present in the HCD and User-Centered Design methodologies such as Institute of Design at Stanford (2013) and Suri (2003). According to Parrish (2006), storytelling is a process that combines analysis and synthesis. The stories are always based on extracted facts of life, as personal experiences or observations, and may even go further. Due to this characteristic, the author claims that storytelling is also the process of discovering facts about the narrator of the story. The stories can be seen as a form of research in which, besides the possible analysis, elements of the world are brought together with imagination. This characteristic makes the stories a source of information that can be used by designers to develop their projects.

In terms of storytelling related to a product, Battarbee (2003) states that the stories of products can provide an understanding of how the product interacts with life in lasting and meaningful relationships, and how these relationships can be corroborated through design. The author emphasizes that storytelling can be very useful in the early stages of product design. According to Lin et al (2011), a story must be narrated (in writing or orally) by the person who experienced the event (orally or writing). Otherwise, if told by someone else—even if told truthfully and with emotion—the audience can easily notice that it is not a first hand account.

For this research, the story writing method was used, whereby the user is the author of the stories. This was used as a way to gather information about the product from the group of children through a proposed these that was generic and comprehensive. Thus, the following title was established: "Me and my eyeglasses".

The participants were children of both genders using prescription glasses, in the 7-11 age group; therefore, belonging to the stage of development called concrete operations, as classified by Jean Piaget (1896 - 1980) (Terra, 2013). Another determining factor in this age group was the need for the children to be literate, to make the proposed method possible.

The study included a total of thirty participants from the southeast and northeast regions of Brazil, fifteen girls and fifteen boys.

The first procedure was an introductory document, which was also a step-by-step method with some important observations. The method was applied at a time when the child was receptive to writing; adults were in charge of providing the children with a lined sheet of paper and a pencil and to simply tell them the title of the story they were asked to write. The adults were required not to influence the children or give them any ideas. The children were free to write as much as they wanted and the activity was considered finished when they stopped writing.

The data was collected by a) sending an email to the children's guardians, so they could apply and then return the stories; and b) by visiting three schools—one public and two private—which authorized the application of the method on the students who wear eyeglasses.

DATA ANALYSIS

To analyze the stories, topics were defined from similar subjects present in their stories. The technique used was based on cluster analysis proposed by Mingoti (2005, pp.155-156) in which the objective is to divide the elements of the sample or population into groups so that the elements belonging to the same group are similar.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The stories' content analysis resulted in eight main topics according to the statements found in the written stories. These topics were grouped into four other categories created to subsidy a better understanding of the topics and the practical application (Table 1). The difference between the information provided by each gender was observed in each topic since the eyeglasses for boys and girls have formal differences.

TOPICS		DIRECT QUOTES	CATEGORY	SOME INSIGHTS ABOUT EYEGLASSES DESIGN
1	Usability	<p>“...I wear eyeglasses, I don't like to walking around with them ...”</p> <p>“... I adore my eyeglasses...”</p>	Functional	<p>Even with negative aspects, the majority declares that they like to use the product.</p> <p>Discomfort caused by disease.</p> <p>Perceived benefit of using.</p>
2	Symptoms of not using the product	<p>“... (I) remember that everyday in class I force my eyes, only to see what was written on blackboard...”</p> <p>“... I wear eyeglasses because my eyes sting and it gives me a headache...”</p>		
3	Feelings about wearing the product	<p>“...when I wear eyeglasses everything gets renewed, everything become colorful...”</p>		
4	Product Characteristics	<p>“...it was black and rounded, but I did not wear it much...”</p> <p>“...mine are batman eyeglasses...”</p> <p>“... my eyeglasses are purple light and have pink flowers...”</p> <p>“...I think my eyeglasses are pretty...”</p> <p>“...my eyeglasses are ugly...”</p>	Formal	<p>Girls talked more about product characteristics than boys.</p> <p>The most talked about characteristics by girls were: color/brand, overall look/shape and material, in this order.</p> <p>The characteristics highlighted by boys were: overall look/brand and shape, in this order.</p> <p>They worry about maintenance, loss, cleaning and damage.</p>
5	Product Care	<p>“... I hate it when they get dirty ... it is horrible to clean them...”</p> <p>“...they break if dropped on the floor, they get scratched, you have to take care of them and clean them...”</p>		
6	Medical exam and eye disease	<p>“...my father took me to an appointment and the doctor said – “he needs eyeglasses!”...”</p> <p>“...but to wear them you have to have an eye-test to know what your lens power is...”</p> <p>“...the first ophthalmologists looked, did a test with only one instrument and said – this girl is myopic...”</p>	Medical	<p>Boys talked more about the visit and experience of medical exams.</p> <p>The same number of boys and girls mentioned their eye disease.</p>
7	Third party opinion	<p>“...I have never been bullied because of my glasses, but I know girls who suffer a lot because of it...”</p> <p>“... sometimes wearing glasses can be bad, you can be excluded and people can call you a nerd...”</p> <p>“...my mother and father also wear them (glasses), so sometimes I wear them...”</p> <p>“... but my mother asks me to wear them (glasses).”</p>	Reflexive	<p>The influence of family and friends appear equally.</p> <p>Few children talked about their appearance and their perception of themselves wearing glasses.</p>
8	Appearance wearing eye-glasses	<p>“... I think I look very weird wearing eyeglasses...”</p> <p>“... we look different wearing eyeglasses, I become more elegant and charming...”</p>		

Table 1. Table relating the topics grouped in categories, some insights gathered from those and also some direct quotes from the children stories.

Source: Authors (2014)

Functional Category

This category deals with functionality and correction issues in eyeglasses. The three topics were mentioned very frequently in the stories, which demonstrates the strong association of the product with its corrective function and the participants' perceptions of when the product is used or not.

The *Usability* topic was observed by both genders equally. In their stories, most children talked about whether they liked wearing glasses and the majority mentioned positive associations. Therefore, generally good product acceptance was observed, but there is still a declared aversion by some users.

In the *Symptoms of not using the product* topic, we observed that almost half of the participants talked about the many discomforts caused by refractive errors, when eyeglasses are not used. On the other hand, in the *Feelings about wearing the product* topic, most participants made a point of mentioning the benefits that the eyeglasses provide when used.

Formal Category

This category is related to the formal characteristics of the eyeglasses. In general, the two topics in this category did not appear in the texts as much as the topics relating to the functional categories, but had a good representation nonetheless. The content of the formal category is very objective and it is most directly applied by designers.

Among the *Product Characteristics* mentioned, we can see that more girls than boys talked about this topic. The most commonly talked about characteristics by girls were related to the colors of the frames. Also, positive comments were made about the product's overall look and mention of the brand was made. The shape and material of the product were less often mentioned by both genders. Among boys, the characteristics most often mentioned were the overall look (regardless of whether their comments were positive or negative), and the brand, with the same frequency and number of mentions.

The *Product Care* topic was not mentioned many times. However, the existing comments addressed specific and detailed aspects that are experienced by users. These data serve as indicative for improving issues in eyeglass designs, such as material resistance, maintenance, loss and cleaning for example.

Medical Category

The children wrote about the experience of the eye-test and their eye problems. This content is related and reinforces the functional categories of the product, since the children mentioned the reason or the time when they began to wear the product. Among the narratives, we did not find any aversion to the experience of going to the doctor and doing the tests.

The eye-test experience was more commonly mentioned by boys, and those who wrote about the visit to the ophthalmologist also wrote about their ophthalmic problems. In their stories, girls talked more about their ophthalmic problem than the eye-test.

Reflexive Category

The topics in this category report on how users see themselves and are seen when wearing the product. The stories in which the children are concerned about being perceived as good-looking, wearing eyeglasses is accompanied by negative reports about third party opinions. Therefore, in these cases, the *Appearance* topic can be interpreted as user self-assertion in defense to a bad review and stigma product. Regarding family opinion, there are cases in which the discourse of being good-looking wearing glasses is tied to parents also wearing eyeglasses. In this case, the fact that parents are wearers serves as a stimulus or positive influence for children. In general, most children mentioned the opinion and influence of others on wearing the product, as related or not with appearance, demonstrating that for some of them, there is still some concern about the stigma of wearing glasses.

The *Third Party Opinion* topic was often mentioned by both genders. Worrying about their friends' opinions, the stories were mostly related to the stigma associated to wearing the product, even when there were reports of encouragement aimed to increase the self-esteem of the user. This implied that there was a negative feeling related to wearing the product. The family was mentioned when they talked about their parents' encouragement and request that they wear the product, and when their relatives were an inspiration and a motivational force, in cases whereby they too were users.

The *Appearance* topic was not mentioned much, but with the same frequency by both genders. This demonstrates the need for self-evaluation, positive or negative, on what one looks like wearing the product. The low occurrence of the subject can also be interpreted as indicative of the product being perceived as an accessory.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

After discussing the categories, it is important to analyze the style and organization of the narratives obtained with the method. The storytelling method was applied with a broad title, enabling the children to produce any kind of story about the product, including fantastic and ludic narratives. However, in the thirty stories analyzed, from geographically distinct locations, the contents about the product discussed real issues, like emotions and experiences related to its use. This narrative structure demonstrates that eyeglasses were thought of by the children as a very pragmatic object, showing that the children think of their glasses in terms of a corrective item rather than an accessory.

The data (topics and categories) is important for the entire project because it shows the user's subjective perception of the product. The Human Center Design methodology provides data which reflects the desires and needs of users, so storytelling was an appropriate method to encourage children to write their own stories entirely without being influenced by an adult; thus, allowing for spontaneous topics to arise, without

inducing a specific subject and also bringing unusual and unexpected themes.

Also, the subjective data gathered with this method, guided the research and helped to create data for another collection method with children that is more directed and objective. Therefore, the results of those two methods with different characteristics will be analyzed and combined to define final and complete information from the children about the design guidelines for their eyeglasses.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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TRIGGERS

USING DESIGN TO CHANGE HABITS

Andrew Shea

✉ ashea18@pratt.edu

ABSTRACT

Triggers was a 16-week classroom investigation into how to use communication design to change habits. Students in this graduate-level class partnered with a classmate, identified habit loops, prototyped and tested possible solutions that could bring awareness to the problem (making design changes as needed), tracked the quantitative and/or qualitative changes, and measured how behavior changed. Topics ranged from procrastination, creative confidence, eating less meat, calling your mom more often, doodling in more productive ways, and grinding your teeth less.

Students focused on a human-centered, holistic, and empathic approach, and applied Design Thinking methodologies to their challenge. Students had an adequate amount of time to understand how design can change behaviors and some outlined their methodology in the form of a toolkit that others might use to change their habits.

KEYWORDS: *habits, behavior change, multi-disciplinary, toolkits, strategies*

INTRODUCTION

Graphic designers work in an ephemeral media. Unlike architects and urban planners who shape public spaces, and product and industrial designers who create useable objects, the passive nature of communication design makes its success inherently more difficult to measure. Nevertheless, graphic designers follow user-centered processes that can help them work across disciplines to find solutions to challenges of various scales. This inspired us to challenge our students to use graphic design in ways that might change a personal habit. We hoped that by focusing on problems at a small, personal scale, we could better-assess the influence that communication design has on people. We were also inspired by the range of recent insights about the nature of how habits form and can be changed.

RESEARCH

First, Wendy Woods and David Neal are two behavioral psychologists who have written about the role that environments play in our habits. According to their research, 45 percent of our daily behavior is repeated. Woods says that we are "integrated" with our environment because we spend most of

our time in just a few locations, whether that be at home, work, school, or in transit, where it becomes easy to form complex routines and a myriad of habits. We used this insight to encourage our students to consider the spaces where they spend most of their time and also referenced *The Power of Habit: Why We Do What We Do in Life and Business*,² a book by journalist Charles Duhigg, in which he examined personal, corporate, and societal habits. Duhigg writes about how many problems start as individual actions that often go on to form habits, which are then reinforced by a myriad of seemingly harmless factors. All of which make up a "habit loop."

Figure 1: The Habit Loop

"Habit Loop" is Duhigg's term and it consists of a cue, a routine, and a reward. Duhigg thoroughly explains these in his book and uses them to illustrate how we might manipulate our habits. Cues are the factors that trigger our habits: particular locations, times, emotional states, other people, or an action that immediately precedes the habit. Routines are the behaviors you want to change. Rewards satisfy the cravings that drive our behaviors.

ASSIGNMENT

This project took place in a class, which involves students applying design-thinking methodologies to social issues. This particular class aimed to transform the behaviors of individuals and communities in desirable ways while creating meaningful experiences and interactions. For this particular project, students were charged with the task of identifying one habit they wanted to stop or start.

We called the project "Triggers."

PROCESS

We often feel challenged by the short amount of time that a 16-week semester allows for projects to evolve. We wanted students to have the whole semester to work on the project in hopes that the extra time would produce more insights and better results overall. So we started the project on the very first class. Students had about 15 minutes to choose one habit that they wanted to either stop or start, then they partnered up with a classmate who they would work with during the whole term. The first couple of weeks were dedicated to defining the problem. Part of this included understanding what we called the "ecosystem" of the habit, or all of the factors that might contribute to it. We led "brainwalking" exercises, which are more dynamic forms of brainstorming and mind-mapping. Students jotted down the habit that they wanted to stop or start on a long sheet of paper and then rotated to each different habit and added what they know about the habit. We expected that a lot of students would focus on health or hygiene-related topics, but were happy to see a broad range of issues: procrastination, eating less meat, creative confidence, doodling in more productive ways, one pair of students focused on calling their mom more often, productivity, and grinding teeth less, for example. On the third week, students came to class with an infographic poster that described their partner's habit and how they planned to use design to help their partner. The impressive range of posters each identified the "habit loops" and their specific opportunities to disrupt the habits (or create new ones in some cases).

During most of the semester, students prototyped potential design solutions that could bring awareness to the problem (making design changes as needed), tracked and measured the quantitative and/or qualitative changes that took place, assessed how well the solutions worked and, in some cases, redefined their project altogether because of what they

Figure 2: Measuring Behavior Change

learned along the way. Students customized their design solutions to meet the unique patterns of their partners' lives. Some students used analog strategies to effectively collect the kind of information that can help them better understand the habit while tracking and measuring their partners' change in behavior, while others used digital technologies like websites and apps.

When we discussed the projects with just a few weeks left in the semester, it was clear that all students changed in some way because of the project. We asked them to tell the story of their project and found that simply building awareness about the habit helped them to change their behavior: by understanding the habit loop, designing objects and systems to address challenges, and regularly tracking the change in their behavior. In fact, by simply summarizing the outcomes of their collaborations, they discovered even more nuances about their habit and projects. Here are five of those twenty projects.

PROJECTS

Putting a Halt on Teeth Grinding

Our first student grinds his teeth sometimes, but he would not consider it a habit, just something that happens if he is more tired than normal, or if he's trying to choke down words that he does not want to come out. He realized that his partner grinds his teeth when he is stressed. So, our first student designed a facial massage technique book to help him distress, as well as a teeth-grinding logbook.

Figure 3: Putting a Halt on Teeth Grinding

Figure 4: Stop Interrupting People

Figure 5: Remember to Call Your Mom

Figure 6: Produce Less Trash

Figure 7: From Meat Lover to Flexitarian

Stop Interrupting People

Our second student has a habit that can sometimes be annoying; she interrupts people during conversations. She was completely oblivious to this, so her partner designed a fun and unique way to warrant her attention, by creating a mobile clicker app that would allow her to log how many times she would do this in a day. She also created a citation packet that her friends could give to her whenever she would interrupt them.

Remember to Call Your Mom

As children we live with and depend on our mothers to teach us how to navigate daily life. Soon enough, however, we grow up and move away; our routine interactions fade. How can we maintain a meaningful relationship with our long-distance moms? For this third project, two students created a diary log that helps you document your conversations with your mom, so that you remember why you should keep calling.

Produce Less Trash

As an action becomes routine, the habit shapes identity. By changing his habit, our fourth student, who developed the routine of producing too much trash, sought to create a new identity. By using social media, his desires and shopping patterns were analyzed and new habits formed.

From Meat Lover to Flexitarian

Eating meat was our fifth student's dilemma. In order to lessen the guilt trip generated by every meal this project aimed to help him transition to a flexitarian regime, moving his meat-heavy diet in a more vegetarian direction. Going meatless on Mondays, photographing his meals, documenting his struggles and triumphs on a blog and providing recipes were all strategies to help him change his habit.

SCALE

While the scale of these one-to-one projects are small, students learned skills that they can apply to greater social challenges. The variety of these small-scaled projects also serve as a mirror for the range of larger, societal issues that could be addressed, one of which students worked on during the same class. This other project involved students looking at the social behavior of different New York City communities affected by Hurricane Sandy. Their challenge was to use design as a means to promote and encourage preparedness and resiliency efforts within these communities and the students applied the same design strategies from the Triggers project to a wider audience, while also looking for ways to track and measure how people were responding to the designs. While more complex design challenges require a larger set of considerations, we learned that the strategic approach of de-

signing to change behavior (which includes finding ways to track and measure a design's impact) can increase the overall effectiveness and impact of design challenges at any scale.

TOOLKITS

The results of these projects prove design's effectiveness to change and improve behaviors, and they encourage us to continue exploring how design can be used to improve even the small facets of our lives. When students told the story of their project at the end of the semester, some wanted to share what they learned with a wider audience. They summarized their findings and approach in toolkits that others can use to stop and start the same habits.

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FOOD, CULTURE AND IDENTITY

SERVICE DESIGN TOOLS AND METHODS IN A SOCIO-CULTURAL CONTEXT

Heidi Uppa, Marja Seliger, Tania Rodriguez-Kaarto
Aalto University, School of Arts, Design and Architecture
✉ heidi.uppa@aalto.fi, marja.seliger@aalto.fi, tania.rodriguez.garcia@aalto.fi

ABSTRACT

This full day workshop combines different aspects around local food culture and understanding food as a social bond between individuals and groups. The participants will contribute with their food related thoughts, ideas and experiences. They will learn about local food cultures by sharing their food-related stories, memories, emotions, ideas and rituals with each other. In the workshop, service design-related design game methods and tools will be tested in a food context and in a different cultural environment than originally designed for. The presumption is that local solutions are required to solve global problems such as food sustainability. We argue that understanding social identities and values are needed for the creation and appliance of new sustainable food concepts and services. This workshop explores social, emotional and cultural aspects of local food and how food related rituals, memories and tastes bring people together.

KEYWORDS: *food, culture, identity, design, social*

INTRODUCTION

Food sufficiency and sustainability have become one of the major environmental and ecological issues today; a global problem with no simple solutions. Local actions and understanding cultures and identities are needed for offering healthy and sustainable food options in the future. Food is a necessity with important social and cultural aspects. Food traditions play a role in our identity creation process (Gronow 1997) and eating can be seen as a social ritual bonding people together. However, the social aspects of food are not always recognized. In this workshop, service design methods and visual communication tools are used to explore the complexity of the subject and to gain a deeper knowledge and understanding about local food in a social context. This workshop explores how game design methods based on storytelling and narratives are adapted in different cultural environments. The aim is to offer new food related experiences and to gain a deeper understanding about how service design and participatory methods, tools and elements work in different cultural and social contexts.

WORKSHOP GOAL

The aim of the workshop is to test service design related methods and tools in a food culture context. “Identity map” and

“Food concept/Meal design” design games will be used to inspire participants to share their stories, memories, emotions, rituals and values related to food. Participants will learn new aspects of local Colombian food culture(s) as well as understand their own food-related behavior and emotions. They will gain knowledge and experience about service design and participatory methods while interacting with other participants from different cultures and backgrounds.

One goal of the workshop is to test the qualities of the chosen design games and tools and to evaluate how the game concepts, formats and mechanics work in a new context. Using design games as a research method is becoming common and therefore it is important to test their applicability in different cultural and social environments. The crucial question is the validity of the design game concepts and how to develop or adjust them for different cultural contexts. The aim is to learn more about good game facilitation and share the knowledge with the participants.

PREVIOUS STUDIES

This workshop combines elements from design thinking, visual communication, semiotics, service design, game design, social psychology and self-categorization theories (Turner, Hogg, Oakes, Reicher, & Wetherell, 1987). Some previous

research related to consumer behavior in the field of branding and marketing can also be found. This workshop proposal is based on experiences and research done by organizers in the Shape-Sustainable Meal project, which focused on providing sustainable design solutions for lunch caterers in Finland. More info: <http://gdresearch.aalto.fi/site/research/sustainable-meal-communication>

WORKSHOP DETAILS

Length of the workshop: Full day (6 hours)

Location: Cali

Participants: Maximum 24 and minimum 12 participants can be accepted

Requirements for the venue:

- a room large enough for 12–24 people
- tables and chairs to work on (groups of 4–6 people)
- electricity, power bars and cables (for laptops)
- a projector and wall/screen to project on
- access to the internet
- ideally the venue would be close to some local restaurants or food market

All other materials (paper, posters, cards, pens, objects, stickers) will be provided by the workshop organizers. Contact details: Heidi Uppa, heidi.uppa@aalto.fi

Participation

Participants should have an interest in art, design or design research, but no other specific professional or educational experience is required. However, we hope that participants will share a passion for food and culture. Participants are encouraged to bring visual materials (photos, pictures) to the workshop. The materials should be related to their eating habits, memories or cultural traditions.

WORKSHOP SCHEDULE (TENTATIVE)

Full-day workshop with the following schedule outline:

AM: Introduction and Identification Tool

- Introduction to the workshop aims, activities and the schedule.
- Inspirational introduction lecture on “food, culture and identity”.

- Grouping: formation of groups of 4–6 people.
- Group work, part 1: sketching exercise to introduce group members to each other.
- Group work, part 2: discussions about personal eating habits, values and beliefs related to food.

Documentation by using “self identification map” tool.

- Group work, part 3: Idea creation session and choosing a subject for the group exercise by using identification maps. Collection of possible additional materials and visual references for the exercise. Active exploration of the subject.

Lunch Break

(can also be used for material collection and to explore the subject)

PM: Game Session and Presentations

- Group work, part 4: “food concept/meal design” game session.
- Presentations by the groups of their results and insights.
- Final discussions and feedback

AFTER THE WORKSHOP

The organizers will produce a summary of the workshop reflecting the discussions, materials and learning outcomes. The format, contents, distribution and the platform of the summary will be decided in the workshop.

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SUBTHEME 5 Experience and Interaction

Mediated and unmediated experiences between individuals or collectives of people interacting products and services.

Includes these topics:

- Product-service Systems
- Experience Design
- Human Factors & HCI
- Affordances & Semiotics

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TO LEARN IS TO EXPERIENCE: HOW OUR DAILY INTERACTIONS WITH OBJECTS, EVENTS, THE ENVIRONMENT, AND PEOPLE CAN BE A CLASSROOM

Kok Cheow Yeoh

Lecturer, Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore.

✉ kcyeh@ntu.edu.sg

ABSTRACT

Testing a premise put forth by Nathan Shedroff (2001) that there is always an experience created by an object, an event, the environment, and people, this paper is a report for an experimental course at the Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information in Singapore's Nanyang Technological University. Using experience as a form of pedagogical technique in bridging our experience to what could be learned and shared, 144 students are presented with five predetermined categories to choose from, followed by an individual assignment derived from their interpretations of Shedroff's six dimensions of experience. The course is an attempt to add novelty to problem-based learning, which engages students in contextualized and authentic problems with realistic real-world expectations. By adding our common sensorial and cognitive experiences that we come across everyday as a catalyst for learning and discoveries, the students are also exposed to other learning outcomes — creativity, collaboration, team spirit, artistic appreciation, photography, and crafting.

KEYWORDS: *Experience design, experience, curriculum design, experimental, visual communication, graphic design.*

INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

In an era when camera phones and images are ubiquitous, our society is becoming increasingly visually-saturated. The human experience is a process of constant change which is subjected to redefinitions, relocations, and realignments. The need to incorporate a course which takes into consideration our personal experience is not a new approach. Tom Barone (2000) has suggested that the development of a heightened perception could enable us to critically evaluate the cacophonous messages and abundance of images we experience through the various media that constantly assault our senses. Social scientist Denzin (1978) suggested that our social reality is known and understood as a social production in which human beings are capable of producing our own definitions of situations, shaped and guided by our own behaviour, as well as that of others.

According to Nathan Shedroff, Program Chair of Design MBA Programs at California College of the Arts in San Francisco, California, an effective communication occurs when form and content are contextually engaged in a message carried over time and medium in either digital, physical, or natural formats. To him, our experience is a personal connection with the moment and every aspect of living is an experience,

whether we are the creators or simply chance participants. Because not all experiences are created equally and they must compete for our attention, a profound reaction is initiated when our beliefs and expectations are confronted (Shedroff, p.6). This is partly due to the fact that our experience is constantly shaped by our definitions and interactions with objects, people, events, and ideas that carry symbolic meanings which arise as a result of the interactions.

In today's multimedia and predominantly visually-oriented environment, the importance of visuals as a communication tool has grown and expanded over the years (Goldberg, 1991). The importance of visual communication has grown exponentially especially since the growth of the internet, which is regarded as a visual medium (Kim & Chung, 2012). Not just visual communication specialists are expected to work in multimedia platforms, but ordinary citizens are actively involved in using visuals to communicate. Such an impact, coupled with the rapid development of technologies leading to the convergence of media, further pushes for mass communication schools to acknowledge and revisit the courses they offer. However, according to Moriarty and Barbatsis (2005), establishing an adequate curriculum has always been a challenge for educators due to the broad and interdisciplinary nature of visual communication, which ranges from visual perceptions

to how images are visually and cognitively processed through the human eyes and brain (Barry, 2005), to inquiries about visual culture within specific social and cultural dimensions (O'Donnell, 2005).

ABOUT CREATIVE VISUAL EXPERIENCE AND DESIGN

Design pedagogy consists not only of the methods of learning and teaching but also the skills necessary to the practice of design. Using our experience as a platform for learning is the idea behind this reflective and hands-on approach to a visual communication course which recognizes that there is always an experience created by an object, an event, the environment, and people we come in contact with. These interacting elements play a part in contributing to our overall experience. The 'Creative Visual Experience and Design' course was launched in January 2012 as an attempt to establish an adequate visual communication curriculum at the Wee Kim Wee School of Communication and Information, Nanyang Technological University in Singapore. The course is based mainly on the premise put forth by Nathan Shedroff by orienting students in five pre-determined categories derived from Shedroff's six dimensions of experience (refer to figure 1) as outlined in his book, *Experience Design 1.1: A Manifesto for the design of experiences* (p. 4).

The five categories (see table 1) are derived from the six dimensions, and the justifications of the predetermined are further elaborated 'Group Assignment'. There are two components in the course which each student must fulfill: a group and an individual assignment. Depending on the final enrolment, students are divided into groups of 3-5 students per group. Each group must ensure that the following sections are covered/touched upon, as their individual assignment is based on a written report with the following components: Introduction (5%), Research components (20%), Observations (20%), Examples (30%), and Interpretation (meaning) (25%).

For the duration of 13 weeks, 144 students are exposed to the six dimensions via a 3-hour lecture each week for up to six weeks. Interspersed within the weeks are groups of students that prepare for their presentations, while more groups are exposed to other dimensions in preparing for their upcoming

Figure 1. The six dimensions of experience as outlined by Nathan Shedroff.

presentations. The class sessions are arranged with lectures for one week followed by student group presentations the following week.

GROUP ASSIGNMENTS

In this section, the five predetermined categories which resulted in the varying topics proposed by each group are listed and their findings summarized.

A Colorful Experience

Our most dominant sense, sight, becomes the trigger for a colourful experience. Colors, as strategic and functional triggers can create reflectivity, visibility, and contrast. Colors are successful in enhancing legibility to entice people, communicate concepts, or to convey a feeling or emotion (Triedman & Cullen, 2002). Six groups of students (n=28) seek to discover crucial sensorial and cognitive triggers in colors. By exploring various topics, such as the public housing estates of Singapore (Housing Development Board), cigars, popular television characters for kids with superheroes dressed in colorful outfits, colors that the fashion industry adores, as well as the absence of color, the students highlight how colors are used

Categories	No. of groups	No. of 3 students per group	No. of 4 students per group	No. of 5 students per group	Total
A Colorful Experience	6	1	0	5	28
A Designed World	7	4	2	1	25
Repetitive Things	6	1	1	4	27
Things Beautiful	7	0	1	6	34
Minimalistic	7	2	1	4	30
Total number of students enrolled					144

Table 1. The five predetermined categories assigned and number of students grouped per category.

to reinforce the identity of a company or an entity in ways that bolster a brand's presence. Inadvertently, this also introduces aspects of marketing in which colors have become a commodity that can be used to market things and services in ways that change our perceptions. The absence of colors is explored where food and beverage companies in Singapore daringly use very minimal or neutral colors in their interiors and exteriors to evoke a minimalistic yet sophisticated awe in the minds of their customers. Appealing to our visual and olfactory senses, both natural and artificial colors are found in foods which affect the way foods are presented and perceived. Below are the numbers of the groups and the selection of topics:

GROUP 1: Colorful HDB flats

GROUP 2: Colorful Cigars

GROUP 3: Colorful Power Rangers

GROUP 4: The Absence of Color

GROUP 5: Colorful Food

GROUP 6: The Colors of Fashion

A Designed World

Historically, design has been part of us. Because of our interactions, our social world consists not of objects that have intrinsic meaning, but rather of objects whose meaning arises from the interactions we have with them. Csikszentmihalyi (1991, p.216) writes that 'creating meaning involves bringing order to the contents of the mind by integrating one's actions into a unified flow experience'. Because every sensory element can trigger meanings in products, services, events, or associated experiences, Shedroff (2001) attests that because these elements that contribute to our experiences are knowable and reproducible, they are also designable. Categorically, there are three types of objects: physical, social, and symbolic (Denzin, 1978). Physical objects are those that may be used in leisure occasions such as balls, bats, craft supplies, and so forth. Social objects are people, including leaders, friends, mothers, and other participants in a program. Symbolic objects are ideas, philosophies, or doctrines which can present possibilities for interactions (Ibid., 1978). In the 'Designed World', seven groups of students (n=25) look around their surroundings to discover how categorically, everything is a physical product designed by someone, which in turn impacts on us as we interact with them.

They present designs viewed from humanistic, decorative, occupational, and functional angles. They also show how a socially-designed world can make our world a better place to live in from a humanistic point of view as well as from a decorative angle, and how design has enriched people's lives from both an 'artistic/aesthetic' angle, to a more 'designerly' one. Operationally or occupationally, spaces such as theme parks, food courts, shopping centers, malls, and more are important places that influence the way we live, work, and commute. Finally, they reveal how daily-designed objects have become so entrenched in our lives that we take certain designs for granted. This is where the functional aspects as opposed to

the aesthetic aspects of design are further explained. Below are the number of groups and the selection of topics:

GROUP 1: Developmental stages of design from Roman era to the present

GROUP 2: Shopping

GROUP 3: Gardens

GROUP 4: Ikea

GROUP 5: Books Actually (A book store)

GROUP 6: Design for the ladies

GROUP 7: Art versus Design

Repetitive Things

When an experience is interactively engaging, we are presented with opportunities to become involved. The elements of interaction span from the ability to control the experience to the amount of feedback we get. Whether we are the creator or co-creator of the experience, experiences that adapt to our needs, abilities, interests, and values are also other forms of interactivity. By combining Shedroff's dimension of 'intensity', which is about engagement and 'interactivity'; in short, involvement, the two dimensions become a framework for five groups of students (n=22) to investigate visual patterns found in various things and to ascertain how patterns can engage or involve us in a non-technical yet interactive way.

They present their observations in various topics ranging from products, rituals, symbols, fashion magazines, and coffee shops. They discuss the elements of design that deal with concerns such as size, shape, color, and texture. Our repetitiveness can be found not just in the objects we design and build, but also in social constructs such as birthdays, weddings, and other rituals that repeat themselves over and over. Other observable patterns are found in objects such as upholstery, rugs, floors, wallpaper, clothing, fabric, tile, mosaics, paintings, and more. These are surfaces on which to compose forms, shapes, and texture, for purposes of ostentation as well as structural enhancements. Below are the number of groups and the selection of topics:

GROUP 1: Repetition in Product Design

GROUP 2: Repetition in Rituals

GROUP 3: Repetitive Symbolic Things

GROUP 4: Repetition in Fashion Magazine

GROUP 5: Repetition in Coffee Shops

Beautiful Things

The flow of time influences our experience of something, and thus is a contributive factor in storytelling and narratives. This is true especially in creating a service-oriented experience where we need to consider the duration of an experience. Unless we consider the larger concept of the human experience, we will miss the opportunities to develop more successful experiences. The timeless concept of beauty has enriched us in many ways. How we decide what is beautiful and our

search for beauty in art, design, and architecture become the quest for seven groups of students (n=34) as they delve into things that are considered beautiful, which is arguably both subjective and interpretive. They investigate how beauty, as an underlying value, can be understood in our search for perfection. The beauty industries have exploited our insecurities and deliver products, services, environments, and events that connect us at a visceral level. Regardless of the price, it seems, we yearn for beauty not just in ourselves but also in animate and inanimate objects. The automotive manufacturers create objects that are sculptural and functional but yet when they are scratched or outdated, they are regarded as imperfect or defective, hence ugly, which is the antithesis of beauty. The groups discuss how the pursuit of beauty has enriched us and what the pursuit of beauty has turned us into. Below are the number of groups and the selection of topics:

GROUP 1: Beauty of Death

GROUP 2: Beautiful Pinnacle @ Duxton (condo-styled apartment complex)

GROUP 3: Beauty in Advertisement

GROUP 4: Perfectly Imperfect

GROUP 5: Beauty in Advertisement

GROUP 6: Beauty in General

GROUP 7: Beautiful Asian Women

Minimalistic

In general, we usually do not trust people who are inconsistent, incoherent, unreliable, or those who exhibit multiple personalities. Breadth, as defined in Shedroff's dimensions, is about consistency throughout all media, channels, and touch-points. In order to create consistency, a good design must tie together a number of elements to create repetitiveness. Basic forms without decoration or simple materials and structures can represent a sense of order. Consistency is probably one of the most cited principles of design. Minimalism as a movement in various forms of art and design can be translated as the work being stripped down to its most fundamental features. A graphic designer who arranges the numerous necessary components to create an impression of extreme simplicity has to ensure that every element and all details are absolutely minimized to achieve a maximum effect. If minimalism is characterized by sparseness and simplicity, is it equal to the notion that 'less is really more'? Eight groups of students (n=32) investigate questions such as: 'Is being minimalistic important?'; and 'Is it true that being complicated is easy, and that being content with less is harder to achieve?' Below are the number of groups and the selection of topics:

GROUP 1: Minimalism in Movies

GROUP 2: Minimalism as a Lifestyle Choice

GROUP 3: Minimalistic Logos

GROUP 4: Minimalism in General

GROUP 5: Minimalistic Logos

GROUP 6: Minimalism: Dialogue in the Dark

GROUP 7: Minimalistic Foods

GROUP 8: Minimalism in General

INDIVIDUAL ASSIGNMENT

The individual assignment is a form of a photo ethnographic study which requires the students to photograph 10 images. The inspiration comes from a question developed by mixing the student's group category with four other group categories to form the following question: 'Where is (the category that the student belongs to) being _____ to create _____ in a _____ manner'. The purpose of the individual assignment is to bring an idea to life by infusing their group experience to one that is uniquely the student's own. The students are given the freedom to mix and match the other four different categories, which they were once excluded from, in order to form a sentence that makes sense to them. However, they must use the category from their group at the beginning of the sentence. To reduce any misinterpretations, the categories with more than one word, such as the 'Colorful Experience', 'A Designed World', 'Repetitive Things', and 'Things Beautiful' are reduced to one single word. For example, a student who belongs in the 'Colorful Experience' category could possibly phrase his/her question into a coherently cogent question such as:

- Where is COLOR being DESIGNED MINIMALLY to create BEAUTY in a REPETITIVE manner?
- Where is COLOR being BEAUTIFULLY REPEATED to create DESIGN in a REPETITIVE manner?
- Where is COLOR being MINIMALLY REPEATED to create BEAUTY in a DESIGNED manner?

The 10 images must be accompanied by an analytical description for each photo. In order to avoid the images being interpreted wrongly or being too vague and abstract, they must exercise care through the use of narratives, limited to a maximum of 100 words per image. Although they may share repeated observations, much like the topics chosen in the groups, students are assured that repetitions in their observations are expected, but that the meaning of their images are contextualized and individualistically interpreted from their own experiences. In this way, even if there are repetitions of topics, every observation is in fact different. They are also allowed to place images next to each other within an image as a way to compare and contrast. The two-in-one image will be considered as one. However, they are advised not to re-arrange, arrange, or digitally manipulate the image, as it is considered as altering reality. But they can enhance the clarity of the image by using relevant software. Since some students are from different faculties who may not have access to professional or proper equipment, they are allowed to use any image-capturing device, including their own smartphones equipped with cameras. The basic requirement is that the image must be clear and not overly pixelated.

EXAMPLES OF STUDENT ANALYSIS OF SELECTED INDIVIDUAL ASSIGNMENTS

In this section, the individual assignments from three students with selected pages from their reports are included with verbatim interpretations. For the purpose of this paper, a colorful experience is chosen to test the “COLOR” category.

Example 1: Where COLOR is DESIGNED BEAUTIFULLY to create MINIMALISM in a REPETITIVE manner

Communication Studies student, Xiu Xian HO, focuses mainly on the variation of colors in a supermarket as well as the way it is designed to create visual beauty and forms of minimalism in a repetitive manner. Local supermarkets such as Fair Price and Cold Storage carry an average of 45,000 items, and by placing them in a systematic order on their shelves these supermarkets are able to accommodate massive amounts of products, executed via the implementation of color and product categorization where the aspect of repetition is portrayed. The differences in colors and display in each aisle also provide consumers with a unique visual experience while shopping.

- The Alluring Entrance

A customer enters a supermarket and is greeted by the prominent display of fruits and vegetables, like that shown in Picture one, above. Shades of bright red, green and orange spread out on the table and vegetables arranged in their packages bring one into a world of freshness and crispness of colour and beauty. The rich spread of fruits arranged neatly with their vibrant colors emphasize the wealth of options available, and make one excited to embark on their shopping journey. Moreover, the different shades of color, separated by the plastic panel, create a picture of minimalism by distinct colours.

Picture 1: usual display of fruits at the entrance of a supermarket.

- The Grid Structure

Most commonly sighted and repeated across the supermarket is the orderly and tightlypacked arrangement of the products. As seen from Picture three, above, placing the rectangular milk cartons side by side generates

a minimalistic display through repeated shapes. Also, there is an equal allocation of space to each flavour, as shown from the white milk taking the left, followed by brown, chocolate, pink strawberry, yellow banana, and lastly green melon. Arranging the milk according to their flavour and space allocation helps to further restrict, and creates a more distinct grid structure. Hence, clever use of repeated shapes and colors can portray the effect of minimalism even in aspects such as the shelving of products in the supermarket.

Picture 2: Grid structured shelving, the main arrangement of products across the store.

- Vivid Tones

Picture shows a shelf commonly found along the aisles of the personal grooming and washing supplies sections. The shampoos belong to the same brand but are different in the color of the bottle, mainly in blue, purple, neon pink, neon green, neon yellow, and orange. The high saturation of these colours is designed in a way to subconsciously remind consumers of the chemicals used in these products. The items are being placed according to their similar shapes and colours, with each occupying their own row. The different colours also represent the different types of shampoo, and hence aid customers in their shopping experience. Moreover, the grid structured shelving once again ties in with the orderly arrangement supermarkets seek.

Picture 3: Saturated colours in relation to chemicals used in certain products, like that of shampoo above

- The Art of Clean Up

Similarly, in the poultry section, the different meat is arranged according to their cuts. For example, in Picture, above, cuts such as prime rib, loin rib, sparerib, and boneless fillet, are put into separate trays. This is alike to the Art of Clean Up, by Swiss artist, Ursus Wehrli, where he takes objects and arranges them by their color, size, shape and type. In this case, the different cuts of meat are sorted into their respective trays, further enhancing the repetition of the shape and shades and tones in each color of the meat.

Picture 4: The Art of Clean Up via the arrangement of the cuts of meat). An adaptation of the Art of Clean Up by Ursus Wehrli.

Example 2: Where COLOURS are being MINIMALLY REPEATED to create DESIGN in a BEAUTIFUL manner

From a practical standpoint, visual communication deals specifically with a variety of practical media which requires educational exposures in typography, graphics, still and moving images, all within a framework of cultural, critical, historical, ethical, and logistical perspectives (Lester, 2010). However, a longhand approach from Sin Yee Lee, a Sociology major, is refreshing as it evokes a hands-on, applied technique reminiscent of a scrapbook. She writes her notes on blue, orange, yellow, and pink and yellow Post-It notes, and arranges the text which describes the images she shot with an instant camera. Bold colorful stripes are positioned in the middle to separate the different pictures shot at different locations in Singapore. She also underlines some words in her reflection, and at times adds emoticons and the shape of heart, sprinkled around different parts of her statements.

- Ministry of Information and Arts Building (MICA) at Clarke Quay Colours are minimally repeated here to communicate a message: This is a unique building! What is it? Oh! It's a MICA! Therefore, the colours used here are more than decoration. Rather they are to guide onlookers and also change the perception of government buildings as dull and serious places. Here, bright colors are used to make a difference in people's perception!

COLOURS are so vibrant here in order to separate the work from the play area. Clarke Quay is located near CBD and many young adults will be found there after work. Therefore, colours from their workplace will not be repeated here as this is where working adults can let their hair down and enjoy themselves after a hard day's work! Also, many colours are used to attract the young and the young at heart! Clarke Quay

- Little India

Located in Little India, this building stood out for the use of extremely bright colours and the lack of repetitive colours. This window was particularly captivating as the window grills were of different colours! This shows the detailedness (sic) of every design. It makes people happy looking at it. I think, it makes people from the inside of the building feel happy looking at happy people.

The clothes we wear today and everyday is a piece of design. Here, colours are hardly repeated and this piece of clothing looks pretty bizarre! (sic). The man whom I bought it from got it from Grateful Dead concert in 1977.

I'll never ever know the authenticity of it and will probably never wear it. However, it will be and is the MOST cool clothing that I will ever own.

Hippie Vest bought from Ebay, found at HOME! (sic).

Example 3: Where COLOUR is being DESIGNED BEAUTIFULLY MINIMAL to create DESIGN in a REPETITIVE manner

Ee Ping Yeoh is a business major who reflects upon everyday things as her theme for her individual assignment. One of the objectives is for students to improve creative thinking by thinking 'outside-the-box', and while the assumption is that everyone is innately creative, the approach to unleash the students' creative potentials is predicated on the fact that he or she must be curiously interested in 'seeing'. By paying attention to her surroundings, she engages in a dialog with herself through a qualitative inquiry process and has created opportunities for interpretations. In addition, she experiments with close-up shots which provide judiciously cropped and selected angles to frame her visual narratives.

This photograph shows part of a mirror surrounded by lights. The white lights glowing in a dimmed environment creates a stark contrast between the colours, which makes the spherical light bulbs more distinct in the image. The light bulbs are placed side by side along the border of the mirror which reveals a repetitive pattern of white spheres in a line. As a result, the pattern of light bulbs frames the mirrors and the contrast of the white lights in a dark place draws attention to the design of the border and mirror.

There is only one main colour, brown, that is used. The wood grains on the surface of the tiles appear as variants of the colour brown which give the colours of the tiles a non-uniform appearance. Hence, by creating uniform shapes out of a material of non-uniform colour and arranging them in an alternating horizontal and vertical pattern, a repetitive design is visualized (sic) where the non-uniform colour adds texture to it. The visual effect invoked by the design involves the tiles being placed in a way that breaks the continuous flow of lines, presenting a weave-like appearance.

This photograph features the skin of a fish and the general colours of the skin are in varied shades of silver and grey which is minimal as the colours originate from the same monochromatic family. The skin of the fish shows recurring and repeated patterns of diamond shapes. Hence, when the use of colours and repetitive patterns come together, it forms the typical appearance of fish skin. This overall design becomes an unmistakable clue for one to identify a fish through the layout of the skin.

In this photograph of wall-mounted cutlery, it is apparent that there are two main colours present, white and silver. The colours used come from the same monochromatic family which gives the overall appearance a polished and formal feel. This is further accentuated by the shiny surfaces of the cutlery. The cutlery are grouped together to form a unit and this is arranged to form a canvas of cutlery set repetition. As such, the colour scheme and replication of the same unit creates an overall structured design.

DISCUSSION

It was observed that during class consultations, some students experience difficulties in finding images that fit and answer all the categories accordingly because they do not necessarily understand how to make the connection between verbal and visual elements. Through consultation sessions, students learned that if they could let go of their inhibitions and fears and trust their intuitions to experience the unknown, they could see many possibilities. Their fear is liberated when students collaborate in groups and realize their individualized assignments towards the end. Collaborations are important, and definable as a process of sharing knowledge and experience by interacting with others to maximize the results of an activity, as well as expanding the knowledge of the individuals who are collaborating (Poggenpohl, 2004). The author of this paper acknowledges that although the catalyst and intellectual reflections are many and varied, the catalyst for collaborative learning can come from each student's own reflections and observations. The categories are purposefully predetermined as a standard rubric to allow room for the students to freely interpret by basing it on their own reflections. The students also learn about various topics in which psychology majors present theoretical models adapted from their courses and share them during their presentations to the whole cohort. Other schools such as Art, Design, and Media students enlighten their fellow classmates with visual analysis of design principles and presentable layout styles.

The competition between groups, especially those within the same category, have contributed to the students' motivations. Having multiple groups has allowed each group to interact with other groups for cross-checking purposes. This approach does have some unique advantages and costs. Perhaps the most significant advantage is that from sharing their group presentations, everyone learns from each other, which usually does not occur in a big class. Since the development of the course will extend over several semesters, any refinement and implementation shall be stand-alone phases for evaluation. This is a common approach used in businesses with large projects, which means that the course will not be the same from semester to semester (Morrell et al., 1993). However, the continuity from phase to phase will be closely scrutinized by the course lecturer to ensure consistency in achieving the objectives of the course, which essentially is about getting students to 'experience'. Students have a general understanding of what the assignment expectations are but a considerable emphasis is placed upon ascertaining other details which can contribute to their overall learning experience.

CONCLUSION

In general, this course is about exploring experiences and how they affect us. The catalysts for intellectual stimulation can come from a variety of sources, and our daily experience is a valuable resource to tap into as a learning mechanism. According to Nobel Prize winning psychologist Daniel Kahneman, our

past experiences are almost entirely determined by two things: how the experiences felt when they were at their peak (best or worst), and how they felt when they ended. Through group presentations, the students' collective experience was shared and as they were exposed to their experiences, they also learn about creativity, collaboration, artistic appreciation, photography, and crafting. Every choice we make becomes an enabler for our experiences either in supporting or eroding the meaning, which is influenced, not just across national boundaries, but also across age, gender, and other distinctions. They ebb and flow over time and are constantly changing, responding to situations and are influenced by styles, tastes, and trends of our society. Experience is a connection to all aspects of living as it simultaneously helps us to be in the moment. As we make connections and relationships with diverse elements, our experiences can act as a depository of 'raw materials' that can contribute to the learning process in a personal and endearing way.

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APPEARANCES CAN BE DECEIVING. THE PORTAYAL OF WEIGHT AND EMBODIED MEANING PORTRAYAL IN PRODUCT DESIGN

Thomas van Rompay, Francien Verdenius, Vanessa Okken and Ad Pruyn

University of Twente

✉ t.j.l.vanrompay@utwente.nl, f.e.verdenius@alumnus.utwente.nl, v.s.okken@utwente.nl, a.t.h.pruyn@utwente.nl

ABSTRACT

First impressions often arise from visual perceptions of product appearance, later to be followed by multisensory impressions involving touch and haptic sensations. These subsequent sensations may sometimes reinforce impressions generated by product appearance, but lead to disappointment when expectations are not met. In this paper, the relationship between weight, product evaluation, and consumer personality is tested. Based on the embodied cognition framework, it is argued that a potential pitfall of downsizing consumer electronics consists in accompanied weight reductions, inspiring perceptions of products as cheap and flimsy. In order to substantiate this claim, in study 1, a vision-only study was conducted, clearly demonstrating that people prefer compact, slender product variants over more voluminous versions. In study 2, actual dummy phones were used and product weight was manipulated independently from product appearance. Results show that lightweight variants may reduce value perceptions and product appeal, but that this effect varies with consumer personality.

KEYWORDS: *embodied cognition, product appearance, haptic sensations, value perceptions, personality*

INTRODUCTION

Imagine seeing a mobile phone advertised online; it looks attractive, it just came out, and the brand happens to be the brand of your choice. Hence, you decide to visit your local retailer and eagerly wait to take it home. But as the phone is handed to you, you cannot help but feel disappointed; it sure looks nice, but it feels cheap. In fact, it feels so lightweight you almost get the impression that there is only a cover and nothing underneath. You go home and decide never again to make your purchase decision online, but always visit a local retailer first, as you did this time.

As opportunities for differentiation on traditional grounds such as practical functioning, quality, and price diminish, product developers and marketeers increasingly appeal to experiential aspects of product experience in order to seduce and persuade consumers. In such endeavors, product design often takes center stage as it is the most direct source for communicating experiential benefits. Hence, in the above example, the phone's robust and dark appearance may be stressed in order to convey an image of ruggedness or coolness so as to appeal to specific consumer segments. Usually, focus is on the visual aspects of product appearance since these are generally considered the most important with re-

spect to purchase decisions (e.g., Bloch, 1995). In addition, it is, so far, the only product dimension that allows for presentation in the online context.

However, a considerable body of research testifies to the importance of multi-sensory input in the context of product experience (Spence & Gallance, 2011). Also, when looking at our own lives, we may find that memorable events may not only involve memory for visual aspects but also recollections of a specific smell (e.g., the smell of an advancing summer), sound (music playing in the background) or touch (the soft texture of a blouse resting on one's shoulders). What these examples suggest is that consumers not only consider visual aspects when evaluating product episodes in terms of their experiential benefits but non-visual aspects as well. Additionally, consumers may use sensations from multiple cues in order to obtain a more complete picture of the product involved. For instance, Peck and Childers (2003) showed that shoppers more readily understand and form confident impressions about products with which they physically interact with, a finding in line with the examples painted above.

This research seeks to explore the role of product weight in product evaluations. Inspired by studies addressing the relationship between weight and evaluations of value, here it is proposed that although reductions in weight may to a certain

extent be desirable, especially so for portable products such as mobile phones, excessive weight reductions inspire perceptions of flimsiness or cheapness. In addition to exploring the interplay of weight and a product's visual appearance, the current research also takes into account consumer personality and questions whether weight is more important to some consumers than to others. Specifically, in figurative language use, optimism is often equated with lightness whereas negativism is usually equated with heaviness, inspiring the prediction that effects of product weight vary with participants' positive-mindedness.

To explore these issues, two studies are reported. In study 1, the influence of product downsizing was assessed in an online (vision-only) context. Hence, in this study, participants could only base their evaluations on visual information. In study 2, product appearance and product weight were independently manipulated using actual dummy phones in order to explore their interactions and relative importance with respect to consumer preference and value perceptions. In both studies, mobile phones were used as stimulus materials for the following reasons. Firstly, due to their portable and 'hand-held' characteristics, both dimensions are important in interactions with these products. Secondly, focus has nonetheless been on visual appearances in promotional efforts, amongst others resulting in downsizing of size parameters (further boosted by technological developments allowing for such downsizing). Thirdly, as discussed, mobile phones are frequently sold and bought in the online context where multisensory input is lacking. Before presenting the details of these studies, first we will present a brief overview of research addressing the relationship between weight and consumer evaluations.

WEIGHT AND IMPORTANCE: AN EMBODIED PERSPECTIVE

A key finding of research in embodied cognition holds that many affective or abstract concepts are rooted in people's embodied interactions with the environment and objects therein (Johnson, 1987; Lakoff & Johnson, 1999). For instance, affection and intimacy may be talked about in terms of warmth (e.g., a 'cold' person or a 'warm' embrace). Such couplings can be traced to early-life embodied interactions in which experiencing warmth and intimacy are part of the same interaction (e.g., a young child experiencing intimacy and affection in his mother's warm embrace; Bargh & Shalev, 2012; Grady, 1997). In a similar manner, ease of social interactions and personality may be talked about in terms of material properties such as roughness or smoothness (e.g., a *smooth* interaction or *rough* person). Of particular importance for the current undertaking, importance, seriousness, and value are often conveyed in terms of weight-related constructs (e.g., a 'weighty' issue or thinking 'lightheartedly'). These latter relationships are embodied because they are grounded in correlations between object weight and value judgments in our physical interactions with the environment and objects

therein (with objects of greater weight generally being more important and valuable).

Grady's (1997) conflation theory holds that in the early stages of life, the two domains of an embodied metaphor (e.g., weight and value in the current research) are fused in experience. Hence, to a newborn or young child, objects and people of great size and weight (e.g., her parents, the garden fence or the table in the dining room) are 'automatically' perceived as valuable, important and impressive. Naturally, later in life, this tight coupling between the two domains loosens, and the child may find that things of little weight may be valuable just the same (and vice versa). Nonetheless, the coupling between the two domains persists (at least to some extent) as evidenced by use. In sum, what these examples revolving around warmth, material texture and weight show is that recurrent embodied interactions in and with the environment are at the basis of more abstract notions such as affection, ease of social interactions, and value.

Importantly, such relationships are not mere linguistic phenomena but lie at the basis of cognition in general. Of special relevance to the present context, Ackermann, Nocera, and Bargh (2010) tested influences of weight on impression formation. To this end, passersby evaluated a job candidate by reviewing resumes on either light or heavy clipboards. Findings showed that participants using heavy clipboards rated the candidate more favorably. Specifically, candidates 'presented' on heavy clipboards were perceived as displaying more 'serious' interest in the position. In line with this finding, Jostmann, Lakens, and Schubert (2009) showed that holding a heavy clipboard increased judgments of importance of the issues at stake (e.g., the importance of fair decision-making), and judgments of monetary value. These findings clearly show that the relationship between weight and importance is not a mere linguistic curiosity but is fundamental to cognition in general, and as such weight may (implicitly) inform decision making with respect to product design as well.

CURRENT RESEARCH; VISION VERSUS TOUCH

The importance of weight with respect to decision making notwithstanding, for many electronic consumer appliances, downsizing has been the most important trend in the preceding years, inspired by both usability issues (size reductions to increase portability and comfort thereof) and technological advancements. And as suggested, in the (online) marketing context, it is the only dimension that can be accurately assessed. But what happens when such practices not only lead to more portable and compact designs but to excessively lightweight products as well? The studies described above suggest that this may reduce product value perceptions and consumer liking. However, to date, no research has addressed the relationship between weight and value perception in relation to product experience.

In order to explore the interplay between vision and touch and their relative importance in the design context, two stud-

ies were conducted. In study 1, we sought to verify the presumed importance of product size and thus expected that:

H1: A decrease in mobile phone size positively affects product appeal.

And as downsizing evidences technological innovation and state of the art techniques, we also expected that consumers would more readily associate a smaller product size with enhanced value and thus a higher price:

H2: A decrease in mobile phone size increases perceived value and boosts price expectations.

STUDY 1

Method

- Participants and procedure

58 respondents (26 male, 32 female; mean age: 30.1 years) participated in the study. They were recruited via social networking sites and were asked to fill out an online questionnaire assessing consumers' first impressions of mobile phone prototypes. Upon consent, participants were redirected to a page where they were presented with either a slender, thin variant (Figure 1, left panel) or a more voluminous, thick variant (Figure 1, right panel). In addition to these stationary presentations, a 360-degree rotating animation of the phone was presented to ensure participants could form an accurate impression of the phone's appearance. Next participants filled out an online questionnaire assessing the outcome measures under evaluation.

Figure 1. Mobile phones used in study 1

- Stimulus materials and experimental design

The prototypes (see Figure 1) for this study were modeled in Rhinoceros 4.0 and subsequently printed in 3D by Shapeways (a 3D-printing marketplace). The measurements (117.6/61.5/8.5 mm for the slender variant versus 117.6/61.5/16 mm for the voluminous variant) were based on “candybar” styled mobile phones (popular at the time of these studies), crystallizing in a one-factor (product appearance: slender versus voluminous) between-subjects design.

- Measures

Product appeal was measured with the items “This phone appeals to me”, “This phone is attractive”, “I would consider buying this phone”, and “This is not my type of phone” ($\alpha = .84$). Using 7-point rating scales, participants indicated to what extent they agreed with these statements.

Assessments of product value were tapped with the items “This phone is casual”, “This phone is cheap”, and “This phone is worth paying a premium price for” ($\alpha = .61$). Participants indicated (using 7-points rating scales) to what extent they agreed with these statements.

Participants filled out the expected price (in euro's) prompted by the question ‘if this mobile phone were available in stores, how much would it cost?’.

Results and discussion

An analysis of variance (ANOVA) revealed a significant effect of product appearance on product appeal ($F(1,56) = 30.04$, $p < .001$), indicating that the slender, thin variant triggered a more positive attitude ($M = 4.61$, $SD = 1.15$) compared to the more voluminous, thick variant ($M = 3.00$, $SD = 1.08$).

Likewise, the effect of product appearance on value perceptions reached significance ($F(1,56) = 11.98$, $p < .001$), showing that the slender variant was perceived as more valuable ($M = 3.78$, $M = 1.18$) compared to the thick variant ($M = 2.90$, $M = 0.64$).

In line with the results for value perception, an analysis of variance also revealed a significant effect of product appearance on price expectation ($F(1,56) = 16.88$, $p < .001$), indicating that the slender variant triggered a higher expected price ($M = 354.12$, $SD = 179.13$) compared to the more voluminous variant ($M = 181.32$, $SD = 127.32$).

In line with expectations, these results confirm a general preference for a slender, slim product appearance. In addition, they show that such designs are also perceived as more valuable and costly, as indicated by the fact that price expectations were almost twice as high for the slender variant.

STUDY 2

Having established this general preference for more compact, slender product variants, in a second study, the ‘weight’ factor was introduced. This allows us to assess whether reductions in product weight that often accompany scale reductions are also considered desirable. As outlined earlier, weight reductions may be appraised negatively because of embodied associations triggered by a literal lack of substance. Hence, in study two we independently manipulated visual appearance and weight and again assessed product appeal, value perceptions, and price expectations.

Additionally, we included a short ‘optimism’ personality in-

ventory. Language dealing with positive and negative affect is full of references to lightness and heaviness. Generally, optimism and spiritedness are linked to lightness (e.g., a light-hearted versus a heavyhearted person), problems are often conceptualized as ‘a heavy load to carry’, and a severe depression may likewise be labeled ‘heavy’. Triggered by such language use, here it was predicted that the importance of weight to consumer decision making might vary dependent on whether people tend to experience their world as ‘light’ and obstacles as easy to overcome (i.e., positive-minded participants), or conversely, as ‘heavy’ and obstacles as posing a serious challenge and requiring lots of effort to overcome (i.e., negative-minded participants).

Specifically, research indicates that people tend to prefer products and brands that are congruent with their self-image or personality (Govers & Schoormans, 2005; Hogg, Cox, & Keeling, 1998; Jamal & Goode, 2001; Malhotra, 1988; Sirgy, 1985). For instance, Govers and Schoormans (2005) showed that consumers prefer everyday products (e.g., coffeemakers, soap dispensers, and screwdrivers) with a product personality that matches their self-image (e.g., an extraverted person preferring an outspoken design over a modest design). The basis for such effects can be traced to the fact that products can be considered a material extension of the self (Belk, 1988), and therefore can help express people’s personality to the outside world. Hence:

H3: Lightweight product variants are perceived as less appealing and less valuable compared to heavyweight variants.

H4: These effects are more pronounced for negative-minded (as opposed to positive-minded) consumers.

Method

Participants and procedure. 96 respondents (50 male, 45 female, 1 participant did not reveal gender; mean age: 34.0 years) participated in the study. These participants were recruited at the town center and neighboring companies at a large Dutch city. Upon agreement to participate they were told that the purpose of the study was to assess people’s ‘look and feel’ impressions of early prototypes of mobile phones. Next, they were handed over one of the phone variants, and asked to fill out the questionnaire comprising the dependent measures.

Figure 2. Weight manipulation in study 2

Stimulus materials and experimental design

The phones were identical as in study 1, but this time for each variant, a lightweight and a heavyweight version was created (60 grams versus 180 grams) by inserting fishing sinkers in the phones’ bodies (see Figure 2), resulting in a 2 (product appearance: slender versus voluminous) X 2 (product weight: lightweight versus heavyweight) X 2 (consumer personality: low positivism versus high positivism) factor consideration between subjects design.

Measures

The product appeal ($\alpha = .91$), value perception ($\alpha = .62$), and price expectation measures were identical to study one. In order to measure positive-mindedness, participants were asked to indicate to what extent they considered themselves optimistic and spirited ($r = .50, p < .001$). Responses were recorded on 7-point rating scales. Based on a median split, participants were scored as either low or high on positive-mindedness.

Results

• Product appeal

As in study 1, an analysis of variance revealed a significant effect of product appearance on product appeal ($F(1, 88) = 8.24, p < .01$), indicating that the slender variant was considered more appealing ($M = 4.62, SD = 1.43$) compared to the more voluminous, thick variant ($M = 3.81, SD = 1.30$).

Figure 3. Weight X Personality interactions on product appeal (left panel) and value perception (right panel)

The effect of product weight was also significant ($F(1, 88) = 4.47, p < .05$), indicating that the weighty variant was liked better ($M = 4.44, SD = 1.32$) compared to the lightweight variant ($M = 4.02, SD = 1.48$). Importantly, the interaction between weight and personality also reached significance ($F(1, 88) = 3.97, p < .05$; see Figure 3, left panel).

Simple main effects show that whereas for participants scoring high on positive-mindedness the effect of product weight is not significant ($F < 1, ns$), for participants low on positive-mindedness, the effect of weight is significant, indicating that they have a clear preference for the more weighty variant ($F(1, 88) = 6.67, p = 0.01$).

- Value perception

With respect to value perceptions, an analysis of variance revealed a significant effect of weight ($F(1,88) = 8.65, p < .01$), showing that the weighty variant is perceived as more valuable ($M = 4.28, SD = 1.02$) compared to the lightweight variant ($M = 3.80, SD = 1.10$). This time, the effect of product appearance was not significant ($F(1,88) = 3.09, p = .08$).

The interaction effect between weight and personality is again significant ($F(1,88) = 7.40, p < .01$; see Figure 3, right panel), showing (in line with the results for product appeal) that weight only has an influence for participants scoring low on positivism ($F(1,88) = 12.78, p = .001$). These participants perceive the heavyweight variant as more valuable compared to the lightweight variant. For positive-minded participants, weight does not influence value perceptions ($F < 1, ns$).

Finally, this interaction effect was further qualified by a significant three-way interaction, showing that the effect of weight on value perceptions of participants scoring low on positivism is particularly strong in the slender product appearance condition. Hence, if the phone suggests lightness through its visual appearance, weight is particularly important with respect to value perceptions.

- Price expectation

Finally, an analysis of variance revealed a significant effect of product appearance on price expectation ($F(1,88) = 8.52, p < .01$), indicating that the slender, thin variant triggered a higher expected price ($M = 302.98, SD = 137.30$) compared to the more voluminous variant ($M = 212.45, SD = 145.08$).

The effect of product weight was also significant ($F(1,88) = 5.44, p < .05$), showing that the weighty variant triggered a higher price expectation ($M = 289.43, SD = 160.98$) compared to the lightweight variant ($M = 221.02, SD = 123.25$). The analysis revealed no further interaction effects.

GENERAL DISCUSSION

The theorizing and findings presented in this paper shed light on a largely neglected consequence of downsizing and selection of lightweight materials in design and production of

consumer electronics; a literal loss of substance and resulting consumer skepticism. Inspired by the embodied cognition framework and previous research in cognitive linguistics and the social sciences, we set out to explain why reductions in weight may trigger associations related to value or the lack thereof. Taking into account that ever more products are purchased online, where visual appearances are often the only source of product information, study one demonstrated a general preference for a thin, slender product appearance. Clearly, this is not a surprising finding. After all, mobile phones should be portable, easy to carry in trousers and bags, and unobtrusive. However, decisions based on visual appearances may only be regretted later when products arrive at home and haptic and kinesthetic sensations issuing forth from product interactions enter the picture.

Hence, in study 2 appearance and weight were manipulated independently. As in study 1, product appearance remained the most influential factor with respect to product appeal. However, across the dependent measures, effects of product weight were also significant, and (in line with predictions) particularly strong on value perceptions, indicating that an all too lightweight product may backfire on consumer preference and value perceptions in particular.

Although manipulations of product weight and appearance influenced consumer ratings independently of each other, effects of weight were qualified by consumer personality. Specifically, effects of weight on product appeal and value perceptions only surfaced for participants with a more serious, less optimistic outlook on life. These participants in particular valued the more weighty variants. This finding is remarkable insofar as it suggests that couplings between positivism on the one hand and weight-related constructs on the other are not just a linguistic oddity. The finding that ‘heavy-minded’ participants expressed a preference for more weighty product variants is in line with research and theorizing suggesting that people prefer products that match their own personality or self-image (e.g., Govers & Schoormans, 2005). Obviously, a concern for ‘weighty substance’ may not just follow from personality, but also from situational factors and context of use. For instance, attending an important business meeting or preparing for a job interview may also trigger such concerns. Hence, also depending on context of use (is a mobile phone mainly used for private, business-related, or social ends?), effects of product weight are likely to vary.

Of course, the weighty variants used in current research were still rather lightweight when considering that the iPhone4 (the current model at the time of these studies) weighs in at 137 grams, just 43 grams lighter than the heavyweight version used in the current research. Hence, the heavyweight variants were (in terms of weight) representative of participants’ phones at the time of study, with the lightweight versions arguably experienced as extremely ‘light’. Thus although our findings do not warrant conclusions on absolute or ideal weight in terms of consumer liking and value perceptions, they do reveal a structural relationship between weight and symbolic meaning portrayal that not only structures

language use, but also multi-sensory product experience. Another shortcoming of current research relates to the fact that no actual interactions (e.g., calling, texting, etc.) took place over a prolonged period of time. Arguably, benefits of weight reductions come to the fore with greater clarity after extended use and (for instance) travel.

Thus although no firm conclusions are warranted on the precise implications of the embodied weight-value relationship with respect to product experience and interaction, our findings do strongly suggest to take this easily overlooked factor into account, especially so when considering that weight reductions in the current research did not transpire in heightened product appeal (regardless of consumer personality).

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THE EFFECT OF (UN)PLEASANT SOUNDS ON THE VISUAL AND OVERALL PLEASANTNESS OF PRODUCTS

Elif Özcan
 Hendrik N.J. Schifferstein
 Delft University of Technology
 Faculty of Industrial Design Engineering
 ✉ e.ozcan@tudelft.nl
 ✉ h.n.j.schifferstein@tudelft.nl

ABSTRACT

A product is a multi-sensory object and each sensory property can contribute to the product experience. In this study, we investigated the effect of sound (pleasant, unpleasant, original, and no sound) on the perceived pleasantness of products (i.e., visual pleasantness and overall pleasantness). Results indicate that ratings for visual and overall pleasantness are similar when no sounds are provided with the products (pictures). When participants are provided with sounds corresponding to the product, however, the overall pleasantness ratings decreased and visual pleasantness increased. Furthermore, while original and unpleasant sounds had a negative effect, pleasant sounds had a positive effect on visual and overall pleasantness ratings. We suggest that if efforts are put into improving the sound quality, users will be more pleased and more willing to interact with products.

KEYWORDS: *product sounds, visual pleasantness, overall pleasantness, experiences, audio-visual interactions.*

INTRODUCTION

Imagine yourself in a store where household appliances are sold. You need a coffee maker for your kitchen. There are several of them on the display and you contemplate each coffee maker in terms of its functionality, ease of use, and looks. You finally choose the one that you like the most. After your purchase you take the product home and plug it in. A wild roaring motor sound emitting from the product startles you. You feel disappointed. The unpleasant sound of the product overshadows the pleasant experience you had in choosing it, and the joy anticipated with the use of the product. You are no longer pleased with your choice.

A product inherently facilitates a multi-sensory experience with its visual, auditory, tactile, and chemosensory properties. During everyday product experiences, people perform actions with the product, they perceive sensory stimulation in different modalities, they become aware of the meanings and values they attach to the product, and they can observe any feelings and emotions that are elicited (e.g., Hekkert & Schifferstein, 2008; Özcan & van Egmond, 2009). As far as product aesthetics are concerned, all the sensory modalities can contribute to pleasant experiences (Suzuki et al. 2006; Fenko et al., 2010; Schifferstein & Hekkert, 2011), and con-

sumer products can evoke feelings of intense enjoyment in multiple ways.

Sound may play an important role in how people perceive and judge products on pleasantness. For instance, for an espresso machine or a sports car the quality of the sound clearly contributes to the pleasantness of their usage experience. However, as exemplified above, the pleasantness of electrical products in the absence of sound may not correspond to their pleasantness during use while producing sound. With regard to our daily interactions with products, we can make conceptual distinctions between different kinds of pleasantness judgments. Ideally, *visual pleasantness* judgments are the result of a perceptual process based solely on the product's appearance, whereas *overall pleasantness* judgments reflect an evaluation based on the multisensory interaction including its tactile, haptic, auditory, and chemosensory properties. However, both visual and overall pleasantness judgments may be influenced not only by the presence of the sound but also by the quality of the sound. That is, pleasant product sounds may facilitate a more pleasant experience with a product compared to the unpleasant sounds, which may cause an undesired experience. There is empirical evidence that users can distinguish between visual pleasantness and overall pleasantness. In a study that tackled the effect

of sound on landscape experience, Carles, Barrio and De Luccio (1999) found that pleasantness ratings were higher when landscape sounds or images were rated separately rather than combined. Nonetheless, Carles et al. also showed that sounds with positive associations (e.g., water) increased the overall pleasantness ratings.

Product sounds are mainly consequences of the ways products operate (e.g., motors, fans, and so on) or they give functional feedback on user actions (e.g., button sounds), and they are generally not created to add to the pleasure of product use (Langeveld, et al., 2013). Product sounds are perceived as loud, sharp, and noisy, which leads to unpleasant sensory experiences on psychoacoustical grounds (Özcan, 2008). As a consequence, most product sounds are not evaluated favorably when judged independently (Bijsterveld, 2008; Özcan & van Egmond, 2012). Hence, although product sounds are often necessary in providing information on the stages of product functioning (e.g., washing cycle and spin cycle of washing machines), they are unlikely to enhance overall product pleasantness evaluations if they are perceived as unpleasant.

Sounds in general can affect an experience adversely if listeners do not have control over the production of the sound and its quality (Maris, 2008), which is often the case for product sounds. For example, the loud, rough, and high-pitched sound of a lady epilator can contribute to the negative reactions towards the product itself. An attention-demanding sound is more intrusive and, therefore, considered as less pleasant compared to a non-attention-demanding sound (Bergman et al., 2009). Nonetheless, if we compare the effects of different types of sounds on product experiences, we expect that products with relatively pleasant sounds will evoke more positive overall evaluations than products with relatively unpleasant sounds. For example, Van Balken (2002) showed that improving the auditory quality of coffee machines through mechanical changes shifted the emotional and semantic experiences of products from negative to positive. Similarly, Lageat, Czellar, and Laurent (2003) established links between the acoustical compositions of sounds to users' experiences of luxury. In Spence and Zampini's (2006) study, participants reported that brushing their teeth with an electric toothbrush felt more pleasant and less rough if either the overall sound level was reduced or the high frequency sounds were attenuated. All these studies indicate that by changing the auditory quality of sounds, designers can obtain more pleasant product experiences.

When people encounter products, different sources of sensory stimulation typically are not perceived simultaneously. From a biological perspective, the sensory channels may operate quite independently in terms of stimulus reception, but psychologically the perception of one type of sensory information is likely to partly shape expectations for the other modalities (e.g., Dagman et al., 2010; Schifferstein & Cleiren, 2004). For instance, seeing a large object is likely to lead to the anticipation of perceiving a heavy object when you try

to pick it up, and low-pitched sounds when you put it down. Hence, different types of sensory stimulation seem to go together for everyday products, and people tend to agree on such cross-modal correspondences (e.g., Schifferstein & Tanudjaja, 2004).

Schifferstein et al., (2010) investigated whether and how the overall pleasantness of a multisensory product relates to the pleasantness of its constituents, comprising of different sources of sensory stimulation. In this study, sixteen different product variants (e.g., a table lamp) were evaluated after creating all possible combinations of either a pleasant or unpleasant color (vision), weight distribution (touch), sound and smell. Schifferstein et al. found that the pleasantness of unisensory stimuli influenced the pleasantness of a complex multisensory product only to a very small degree. However, in this particular study the selection of (un)pleasant stimuli for the different sensory modalities was carried out independently for each modality, which may have led to (in)congruous stimulus combinations. Therefore, in the present study the (un)pleasant stimulus sounds are all generated specifically for a particular product context.

This paper studies the effect of (un)pleasant sound on the perceived pleasantness of products. We aim to understand the differences between visual and overall pleasantness judgments involved in product experience, and the kind of effect sound has on these judgments. The experiment measured two dependent variables (visual and overall pleasantness of the product), while one factor (auditory pleasantness) was varied, with four levels of treatment (no-sound (control condition), original sound, pleasant sound, and unpleasant sound).

METHOD

Participants

Sixty participants (34 female and 26 male), students and employees of industrial design engineering at Delft University of Technology, participated. The mean age was 29.7 years. Fifteen participants were randomly assigned to each of the four experimental conditions differing in sound type. All participants reported normal hearing.

Stimuli

In total eight products that are commonly used on a daily basis were chosen for the experiment: dustbuster, epilator, hairdryer, microwave, mixer, shaver, toothbrush, and washing machine. Products were selected to be neither very pleasant nor very unpleasant as regards their visual quality, as confirmed by 25 judges. The lowest rating on a 7-point scale was for the hairdryer (3.72) and the highest rating was for the mixer (5.08). The mean rating for all products was 4.34.

Figure 1. Examples of two product photos used in the study. Dustbuster on the left and epilator on the right. (Philips my shop Nederland have authorized the use of the Philips product photos for our study.)

Visual stimuli

Products were presented as photos (500 x 500 pixels, 150 dpi) on a computer screen. All products were chosen to have a neutral color and were presented on a white background. Brand information was erased. See Figure 1 for two examples (dustbuster and epilator).

Auditory stimuli

Each product was represented by one corresponding product sound, except for the washing machine, which was represented by two different sounds resulting from different operation cycles (i.e., the washing cycle and the spin cycle). Hence, in total nine original product sounds were used that each lasted three seconds. These sounds were recordings of the main functioning mechanisms of the products.

Figure 2. The pleasantness manipulations of sounds presented as barkscales for two products (Dustbuster and Epilator). The full black line indicates the original sounds, the fine dashed line indicates pleasant sounds, and the course dashed line indicates unpleasant sounds.

The pleasantness of the original product sounds was manipulated in Sound Studio three, for three of the four experimental conditions (excluding the no-sound condition): original sound, pleasant sound and unpleasant sound. In total 27 sounds were used (nine products x three pleasantness levels). According to Zwicker & Fastl (2001), the pleasantness of a sound is highly correlated with psychoacoustical parameters: the higher the perceived sharpness or loudness is, the lower the sensory pleasantness is. To make the sounds pleasant, a low-pass filter was used and the amplitude of the lower frequency range of the sounds was slightly increased. To make the sounds unpleasant, a high-pass filter was used and the amplitude of the higher frequency range was slightly increased (see Figure 2 for two examples). During these manipulations, the spectral-temporal composition of a sound was kept as close as possible to the original version of the sounds.

The pleasantness of the manipulated and original sounds was tested in a paired-comparison task by asking 25 judges which sound they thought was the most pleasant. A participant compared three sound pairs for each product type in two presentation orders. Descriptive statistics show that the pleasant sounds were chosen in 53% of the cases ($n = 1350$) as most pleasant, original sounds in 33%, and unpleasant sounds in 14 % of the cases. A repeated measures analysis indicated that the number of choices for pleasant, original, and unpleasant sounds was significantly different from each other [$F(2, 448) = 152.68, p < .001$]. These data confirm that pleasant versions of the sounds were perceived as more pleasant than the original versions, and that original versions were perceived as more pleasant than the unpleasant versions. These preference orders were confirmed at the level of the individual products. However, the manipulations of the hairdryer sounds did not yield the predicted preference order. Pleasant sounds in all hairdryer combinations were chosen in 34% of the cases ($n = 150$) as most pleasant, original sounds in 22%, and unpleasant sounds in 44 % of the cases. Therefore, for the hairdryer the unpleasant version of the sounds was used as the pleasant sound condition, the pleasant version of the sounds was used as the original sound condition, and the original version of the sound was used as the unpleasant sound condition in subsequent analyses.

Procedure

A participant was randomly assigned to any of the four experimental conditions: control condition, original sound condition, pleasant sound condition, and unpleasant sound condition. The visual and auditory stimuli were presented using a specially designed application developed using the Trolltech Qt (Mac OS X — free edition) tool kit. The application ran on a Macintosh iMac Intel Core 2 Duo with 19" screen. For the presentation of the auditory stimuli, external headphones (Sennheiser HD 205) were used. Participants were seated in front of the screen at a distance of approximately 50 cm. They were instructed to rate the products presented as photos on the computer screen on the bases of their visual and overall pleasantness. In all conditions, product types were randomly presented for each participant. The entire experiment was

self-paced and there were no pauses between the rating trials. One rating session for nine products lasted about five minutes.

In the three experimental conditions (original, pleasant, unpleasant), two rating scales (visual pleasantness and overall pleasantness) appeared simultaneously on the screen, but were initially inactive for rating. The participant was asked to listen to the sound of the product presented on the screen. A participant was allowed to listen to the sound more than once while evaluating the pleasantness. All sounds were presented at a similar, comfortable listening level preserving the natural variation in the loudness of sounds. Participants were not allowed to change the sound levels during the experiment.

After a sound was heard, the rating scales became active. Participants first rated the visual pleasantness and then rated the overall pleasantness of the product under the influence of the sound. They were instructed that visual pleasantness was about a sensory judgment based only on the visual quality of the product. For the overall pleasantness rating, a participant was encouraged to imagine the product as a whole with all sensory properties. Ratings were collected on a seven-point Likert scale (one indicating 'not pleasant' and seven indicating 'very pleasant'). In the control condition, the nine rating trials were completed in the absence of a corresponding product sound.

Data analysis

We analyzed the pleasantness responses in SPSS by doubly multivariate repeated measures analysis of variance (Stevens, 2002, p.538). In this analysis, we used the overall and visual pleasantness ratings as the two dependent variables, while Product was a within-participants variable with nine levels, and Condition differed between participants with four levels (control, original, pleasant, unpleasant sound). For the multivariate effects, we report the values of Rao's F, corresponding to Wilks's λ . Significant effects were investigated in more detail by repeated measures analyses for the separate dependent variables. In accordance with Stevens (2002), we corrected the degrees of freedom of the univariate tests with the Greenhouse-Geiser ϵ if $\epsilon < 0.7$, and we averaged the ϵ values from Greenhouse-Geiser and Huynh-Feldt, when $\epsilon > 0.7$. Differences between individual samples were investigated by post hoc t-tests with Bonferroni adjustment.

RESULTS

In the multivariate tests, we found significant effects for Condition ($p < 0.001$), Product ($p < 0.001$), and the Condition \times Product interaction ($p = 0.024$). However, in the univariate significance tests in the separate analyses for the two types of pleasantness judgments, the Condition \times Product interaction did no longer reach significance (overall pleasantness $p > 0.20$; visual pleasantness $p = 0.06$). As we were not primarily interested in the data for the individual products, we decided to perform no additional analyses at the level of the individual products.

If judgments for visual pleasantness are unaffected by the sounds participants hear, we expect responses in the four conditions to be identical. However, the Condition main was statistically significant [$F(3,56) = 3.1, p < 0.05$]. Post-hoc tests with Bonferroni adjustment indicate that these outcomes are mainly due to a difference between the control condition and the pleasant condition ($p < 0.05$). A separate analysis comparing only the three experimental conditions shows no Condition main effect [$F(2,42) = 1.6, p > 0.20$].

We expect the overall pleasantness judgments to be affected by the product sounds, and this is confirmed by a Condition main effect [$F(3,56) = 4.9, p < 0.01$]. Post-hoc tests show differences between the control condition on the one hand and the original and the unpleasant conditions on the other hand ($p < 0.01$ and $p < 0.05$, respectively). Although no other significant differences are found, the separate analysis comparing the three experimental conditions still shows a Condition main effect [$F(2,42) = 3.2, p < 0.05$]. Post hoc analyses show no significant differences between the three conditions, although difference between the original and the pleasant condition just failed to reach significance ($p = 0.055$).

These analyses show that the pleasantness judgments in the control condition, where a product is presented without any sound, differ substantially from those in the three experimental conditions. This suggests that the presence or absence of sounds has an important effect on how judgments of both visual and overall pleasantness are formed. In the absence of sound, participants seem to treat the visual and overall pleasantness judgments similarly: The mean ratings are very similar (3.89 for visual, 4.02 for overall pleasantness) and the Pearson correlation coefficient between the visual and overall pleasantness ratings is 0.32 [$N = 135, p < 0.001$].

In contrast, in the three sound conditions the means for visual pleasantness are consistently higher than the means for overall pleasantness. Surprisingly, although the differences between the three experimental conditions fail to reach statistical significance, the pattern of means is similar for the visual and overall pleasantness judgments, with the means consistently differing about one unit (Figure 3). The Pearson correlation coefficients between visual and overall pleasantness ratings for these three conditions vary between 0.24 and 0.27 ($N = 135, p < 0.01$).

Figure 3. Visual and overall pleasantness ratings (\pm SEM) in the four experimental conditions.

DISCUSSION

The present study shows that ratings for visual and overall pleasantness are similar when no sounds are provided with the visual stimuli (pictures). This is not surprising, since participants are not provided with any non-visual information. Hence, when they judge overall pleasantness, they can only base their judgments on the visual information provided. Therefore, the judgments of visual pleasantness are likely to concur with those of overall pleasantness in this comparison.

When participants are provided with product sounds, however, the overall pleasantness data shows a considerable decrease in pleasantness ratings. This decrease may be due to the low appreciation that is generally found for product sounds. In contrast, visual pleasantness increased when sound was added. Possibly, the pleasantness of the pictures contrasted with the low auditory pleasantness of the sounds, and thereby boosted the visual pleasantness ratings in the study (Anderson, 1973). Alternatively, we might suggest that the addition of sound makes the product come alive, which makes the visual representation more interesting and increases its pleasantness.

The finding that the presentation of product sounds affects both overall and visual pleasantness ratings has implications for product development practice, because it indicates that company decisions should not be based on the evaluation of partial data. If participants in consumer panels are provided with limited information, their judgments will only have limited external validity. As we see in the present study, providing additional sensory (auditory) information has a significant impact on both types of pleasantness judgments.

Similarly, sensory processes are likely to affect consumers' buying processes (Lageat et al., 2003; Spence & Gallace, 2011). Consumers often purchase household appliances in stores in the absence of sound. This is even more so for online shopping experiences. In many cases, people who buy products are able to use only a single sensory modality (i.e., vision) to compare products (see Fenko et al., 2009). Thus, their pleasantness judgments are mainly based on product appearance, which may provide different information than the auditory product properties. Multi-sensory experiences only take place in home environments after product purchase, and people's judgments of product pleasantness may need to be adjusted accordingly. As a consequence, many buyers may be disappointed with their purchase, because even the properties of the relatively pleasant sounds may lead to a decrease in overall product evaluation. Moreover, retailers and producers may be confronted with consumer complaints, as the product may not live up to consumer expectations.

The pleasantness ratings in Figure 3 suggest that the original product sounds and the unpleasant versions we created were about equally unpleasant. This indicates that the sound quality of the products currently found in the market does not enable pleasant auditory experiences. The sounds we used belong to everyday products that people use for mundane tasks such as shaving, drying hair, cooking, washing, and so

on. These unpleasant sounds may lead to momentary annoyance (e.g., preparing a cake with a loud mixer can disturb the user and other people), the desire to avoid using the product again (e.g., an electric toothbrush producing loud and rough sounds does not invite the improvement of personal hygiene), or even health problems due to sensory fatigue (e.g., being exposed to a loud hissing sound from an air-conditioner may eventually lead to health issues). On the positive side, our results suggest that if efforts are put into improving the sound quality, both the visual and the overall experiences with products are enhanced and, consequently, users will be more pleased and willing to interact with the products.

Furthermore, even though intrinsic sound properties for products may generally be evaluated as unpleasant, some cognitive associations may nonetheless be positive and improve product purchase (Özcan, 2014). For instance, a roaring motor sound may evoke associations with being wild and untamable, and may make the user feel adventurous in the context of a motorbike ride. For a user who likes to feel adventurous, using this product may give him more pleasure, in which case this sound may improve his product evaluation. Hence, making use of expressive sound properties may provide an additional route for improvement in the product design (e.g., Ludden & Schifferstein, 2007).

We have shown that there is interplay between the sensory properties of a product (audio-visual) with regard to the experience of pleasantness. However, our manipulations were restricted to the auditory product properties only and we have not manipulated the contribution of visual product properties. A future study could systematically investigate how each sensory property of a product (e.g., visual and auditory) individually contributes to affective product experiences.

One of the limitations of the current study is the participants' lack of physical experience with the product properties tested (i.e., auditory and visual product properties). In other words, participants' judgments on visual and overall pleasantness are based on the photos and recorded sounds of products instead of the products proper (i.e., tangible or physical products). A future study could investigate whether the effects found would persist if participants interacted with physical products (provided that the physical products can be modified in situ in order to produce pleasant as well as unpleasant sounds). Furthermore, other product experiences pertaining to basic affective responses could also be measured as a continuation of the current study. For example, it could be tested whether the product is perceived as pleasing, stimulating or powerful in relation to the interventions caused by the sounds of the products, perhaps even with different degrees of pleasantness.

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LEARNING FROM THE POSITIVE: A STRUCTURED APPROACH TO POSSIBILITY-DRIVEN DESIGN

Simon Jimenez, Anna E. Pohlmeier, Pieter M.A. Desmet
Delft University of Technology, Faculty of Industrial Design Engineering
✉ simonjjaramillo@gmail.com, a.e.pohlmeier@tudelft.nl, p.m.a.desmet@tudelft.nl,
Gerjan Huzen
BMA Ergonomics
✉ g.huzen@bma-ergonomics.com

ABSTRACT

This paper discusses an approach to possibility-driven design as an alternative to traditional problem-driven design approaches. The first parts discuss merits and challenges when designing for possibilities, and present some examples of existing design theories that exemplify the potential contribution of this view on design. Next, a five-staged possibility-driven design process is introduced, in which personal anecdotes are collected, selected, and analysed as a main fuel for the design process. A design case is reported that applied this process to the design of office furniture. A positive, personal anecdote of an office worker about ‘dissolving in the moment’ was selected as the main design theme for designing a novel experience in the office mediated by a chair. The design case is used to discuss details of a possibility-driven design approach. Finally, we reflect on the suitability of the approach for different design scenarios, its limitations, and possible (future) applications.

KEYWORDS: *Possibility-driven design, experience design, methodology, design case, subjective well-being*

INTRODUCTION

Traditional design approaches mostly focus on ‘undesirable’ present situations and envision an ideal future state where these situations are resolved. In the words of Roozenburg and Eekels (1995, P.84), ‘design is a special form of problem solving. We speak of “a problem” when someone wants to reach a goal and the means to do so are not immediately obvious. Problem solving is the process of thought, in which those means are sought intentionally’. There are numerous examples that illustrate this traditional problem-driven view on design, e.g. faster trains to reach our destinations on time, heaters to protect us from the cold, air purifiers to shield our homes from bacteria, paper clips to keep our sheets of paper together. This traditional problem-solving way of reasoning is relevant since it increases the quality and effectiveness of the products and services we all use, seeks to minimize problematic situations that could threaten our well-being, and generally makes our lives ‘easier’ and ‘better’. However, neutralizing the negative by solving our everyday problems does not necessarily mean delivering a positive and worthwhile experience (Desmet &

Hassenzahl, 2012). Focusing on the positive side of the solution spectrum with a possibility-oriented approach promises a fresh perspective on the role of design.

This possibility-driven view on design has recently been proposed in the design research community. In the words of Hekkert and van Dijk (2011, p. 120), ‘a designer’s job is to look for possibilities, and possible futures, instead of simply solve present-day problems’. Similarly, Desmet and Hassenzahl (2012) call for a transition from problem-solving to exploring possibilities in design, which, regarding the end result, parallels a transition from neutralizing the negative to exploring the positive. They see problem-driven design as ‘curing diseases’ and as the management of ‘hygiene’ and ‘enabling’ factors (2012, p.4). In sum, a possibility-oriented approach to design seeks to explore the role of design in the positive space beyond neutrality (Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013). The relevant question for designers is less whether design can create new or support existing possibilities, but rather *how*. How do we design for possibilities? And how does an approach focusing on the introduction of possibilities differ in its process from one focusing on the reduction of problems?

The process of possibility-driven design does not seem as evident and straightforward as its traditional counterpart, and therefore introduces some interesting challenges for the design discipline. In this paper, we focus on the merits and challenges of a possibility-driven design approach and share how we tackled some of the challenges in an illustrative design project. We propose an approach that uses personal anecdotes as a main fuel for the design process; and we outline a possible procedure for the collection, selection, and analysis of these anecdotes. The paper concludes with a critical reflection regarding the suitability of this approach.

The illustrative design case presented in this paper was the first author's graduation project of the 'Integrated Product Design' master's program at the Delft University of Technology, in the Netherlands (Jimenez, 2013). The project was carried out for the office furniture manufacturer BMA Ergonomics in collaboration with the Delft Institute of Positive Design (DIOPD). The project goal was to design a product, product-service combination, and/or office environment focusing primarily on the positive contribution to the workers' subjective well-being.

MERITS WHEN DESIGNING FOR POSSIBILITIES

Possibility-driven design's main value stems from a more positive and optimistic view of everyday life. Design is a discipline with the potential to change our environment and shape our societies. Understanding it exclusively as a way of reducing deficiencies might limit its potential. Consider the example of the Eurostar project given by Rory Sutherland (2012, May 4): 6 million pounds were spent to reduce the journey from London to Paris by 40 minutes. With a reduced amount of this money, he explains, they could have put Wi-Fi on the trains, or even paid supermodels to serve the passengers, and make the journey more enjoyable instead of (just) reducing the journey time. Even though somewhat unrealistic, this example shows how reframing a situation positively extends the capability of design to innovate.

Design for experience offers a multitude of examples that illustrate the value of providing users with positive experiences instead of merely decreasing the likelihood of negative ones. For instance, Desmet and Schifferstein (2011) assembled a collection of 35 experience-driven design projects from the Delft University of Technology that focus on the experiential side of the process, and how these products aim to evoke a 'pleasant' and 'appropriate' experience. Although varying on intentionality and focus, these projects feature an array of examples on how experience design can do more than neutralizing the negative (see also Hassenzahl, 2010). More recently, some authors in the field of positive design — design for human flourishing — have proposed a possibility-driven view of design whose main focus and purpose is the effects of products on individuals' subjective well-being (Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013). The field has its foundations in theories and frameworks of 'positive psychology' and their body of knowledge. Thus, it is not focused on making the lives of miserable people less

miserable by solving their problems, but on creating opportunities to help people flourish. In general, possibility-driven design seems particularly promising when targeting the subjective well-being of individuals and communities (see Ruitenberg & Desmet, 2012; Desmet, 2011).

In a similar way, authors in the fields of innovation and innovation management favour a view of design as an engine for societal, cultural, and economic prosperity (see Buijs, 2012); design as an engine of possibilities. In his famous book, IDEO's CEO Tim Brown (2009), urges for a shift from *design* to *design thinking*, which, he argues, is capable of translating insights into products that will improve lives. This view of innovation has a pronounced emphasis on possibilities and considers the responsibility of designers much greater than solely taking away what bothers people in everyday life.

All authors mentioned above share the underlying view that product design can extend its spectrum to have an even bigger impact, and that possibility-driven design can be a promising road to successful new product development. They support the idea that it might be worthwhile to think beyond directly addressing an insufficiency.

CHALLENGES WHEN DESIGNING FOR POSSIBILITIES

Several challenges can be identified when designing for possibilities. Perhaps the most evident one is the lack of practical knowledge on how to identify and use them in design processes. In the following sections we suggest an approach on how to design based on possibilities. We outline some challenges and how we rose to them in an illustrative design case. This approach makes use of detailed, single incidents from the users' perspective that represent the desirable design goal to determine the underlying and generalizable pattern of one event in order to formulate design specifications that will be applicable to a greater number of users.

The approach, visualised in Figure 1, consists of five main steps. The first step is to learn from positive examples of user experiences by collecting personal anecdotes of the target user group about happy moments; moments that put a smile on peoples' faces (Step 1). This step is based on the idea that possibility-driven design can be inspired by positive 'role models'. These anecdotes are clustered with the use of variables drawn from theory on human experience and wellbeing that is available in (positive) psychology. The resulting happy moment clusters serve as a basis for the selection of the stories to be used in the design process, and provide an overview of the information gathered (Step 2). Next, the selected stories are thoroughly analysed in order to identify general patterns of the experiential narratives (Step 3). These patterns serve as the basis for the ideation phase, ultimately leading to a design proposal (Step 4). Some challenges regarding the evaluation and testing of concepts resulting from possibility-driven design are further discussed (Step 5).

Figure 1. Structure design process

Step 1. Identifying possibilities

A problem, or a problematic situation, has always to do with discontentment about its present state, and a common understanding of the existence of a more desirable one (Roizenburg & Eekels, 1996). If the desirable state is to be achieved by reducing the insufficiencies of the current situation, this negative orientation makes the identification of a solution fairly evident and straightforward, e.g. I want my car to be faster or I don't want water coming into my shoes. However, when talking about possibilities, its open-ended nature makes it more elusive to define, e.g. I want to find possibilities to be a better person. Design problems may not always be as pragmatic as avoiding having wet feet, but they can be inscribed inside certain boundaries, i.e. specifications, that lead to a plausible solution, i.e. absence of the problem's main cause. Possibili-

ties, on the other hand, do not seem as easy to spot as they are not necessarily apparent in the current context and are rather found in the design process itself. Yet, design approaches at hand are limited in providing the tools to identify them.

Removing problems, or repairing the flaws, may make situations neutral but not necessarily good. A similar development can be observed in the field of psychology: positive psychology focuses its efforts on optimal human functioning and on studying what makes life most worth living (Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi, 2000). In other words, the goal is to reach an understanding of how and when people flourish, and not just to ensure the absence of unhappiness. Several studies show that happy people, apart from being blessed with some genetic conditions and having fortunate circumstances, usually engage in (intentional) activities that increase their well-being (Lyubomirsky et al., 2005). Certain activities (e.g. nurturing relations, taking care of one's body, committing to one's goals) have been found to particularly boost peoples' happiness (e.g. Lyubomirsky, 2007), although individuals differ in ways to flourish and to find meaning in their lives.

Accordingly, in the present design case, possibilities were found in peoples' daily life activities or situations that they reported to contribute to their happiness (in context), and analysed in terms of how and why people engage in these activities and situations. We believe that possibilities are there to be found, and moments of happiness represent promising entry points. In order to collect these moments, two methods are suggested for the field study: diary-booklets and interviews. The diary is meant for participants to shortly report positive moments from everyday experiences in the context, and the interview aims to deepen the details of these stories. In the following these steps are illustrated for the design case.

Diary-booklet

The diary-booklet was used to collect moments of happiness of ten office workers during the course of five working days. Furthermore, the diaries were intended to sensitize participants regarding the topic of study, i.e., happiness, and thereby to prepare them for the interview. One of the daily tasks, called 'once upon a smile', formed the basis of the user study (Figure 2). In it, participants were asked to report three 'smiles of the day' — moments when they felt happy and fulfilled — and to summarize them using words, drawings, or any other preferred means of expression. Illustrative examples were given at the beginning of the diary. From the total of 150 assignments, only those assignments were included in the further analysis that were fully completed and that related to incidents on a working day. For 32 responses, this was not the case. Hence, the final sample included 118 assignments

Interview-session

The research material for the interview-session was designed in order to find more details about the stories the participants described in the exercise 'once upon a smile' (Figure 3). A set-up similar to that of generative sessions was designed (see Sanders & Stappers, 2012). 'Creating movie scenes' was used

Once upon a smile (example)

Each day starts with an exercise called 'once upon a smile' (today you just have this exercise to complete). In this exercise I want you to reflect on the things that happened yesterday, or the last time you were at the office, and shortly describe 3 moments when something happened that put a smile on your face. Sounds easy right? I made an **example** for you below!

Figure 2. Example of the exercise 'once upon a smile'.

as a metaphor for the session. This way of recalling events into a graphic way was supposed to a) put the respondents in the event again, so that they would easily recall all the sensations and characteristics of the moment; b) inspire the participants to use more ways of expressing their thoughts; and c) make the participants more comfortable about communicating their personal experiences. However, when the actual session took place, the participants did not feel confident to draw and get involved with these generative tools. It was then decided to let them free to express and communicate their anecdotes in the way they felt more comfortable, which was mostly verbally.

Figure 3. Interview-session

This approach proved valuable as the majority of stories were not related to the work itself that people perform at the office, but rather to small interactions in-between, e.g. social encounters, breaks. This might have been overlooked if the target user group had not been involved in the identification of possibilities.

Step 2. Selecting possibilities

As stated before, the reduction of problems or problematic situations is a typical starting point for many design projects. An agreement of these situations is mostly shared by a group of people. Possibilities do not 'bother us' as problems do, and they certainly do not represent any threat to our well-being. On the contrary, they embody a potential for a 'positive' result that is not as perceptible as the negative result of a problematic situation if not resolved. This makes selecting a possibility over another a more subjective task. How then do we know which possibility to go for?

One dominant theory in positive psychology suggests that subjective well-being is a construct of five distinctive elements; namely, positive emotions, engagement, positive relations, meaning, and accomplishment (abbreviated as PERMA; Seligman, 2011). Seligman suggests that working on each of these constructs can foster well-being, and, accordingly, moments that promote happiness are enclosed inside one or more of these elements. For the approach, it is suggested to cluster the anecdotes by considering the contribution of the moment to each element of the theory (the most dominant one). This step is intended to steer the attention and design efforts towards certain elements of the theory where more anecdotes are present, and to provide an overview of the information gathered. Once this analysis is finished, a number of anecdotes are chosen out of a cluster (consisting of a variety of anecdotes) by considering the richness of the description of the moment (how detailed it is described), how well it represents the cluster as a story in itself, its originality, while at the same time resonating well with familiar experiences, i.e. the feeling of recognition (see Hassenzahl, 2010).

In the design case, many anecdotes were related to the well-being construct of ‘positive relations’; situations where participants reported having a meaningful moment when sharing with colleagues. Four anecdotes were selected from this cluster to further use in the design process. Since this cluster contained stories in which the participants interacted with other colleagues, a fifth anecdote was selected from the cluster ‘positive emotions’ in order to find possibilities in moments of self-indulgence (see Figure 4 for anecdotes selected).

In engineering design, after having outlined a problem statement and a design brief, one important step to address the problem is to turn it into a set of design specifications. These specifications, or design parameters, set the boundaries for the design process, direct the designer towards a feasible solution, and set out guidelines for the selection and evaluation of the final design (see Pahl & Beitz, 1988). Somewhat refined specifications could have facilitated and increased objectivity of the selection process during the design case. Specifications for designing are of relevance in the next step.

Step 3. Aggregating a personal experience to a general pattern

For possibility-driven design, and due to the use of positive anecdotes as carriers of possibilities, we used an experience design approach to infer specifications from the anecdotes, inspired by the work of Hassenzahl et al. (2013). These authors suggest an approach to find patterns underneath autobiographical stories in order to uncover the ‘mechanism of the experience’; the elements that make it resonate. They propose the identification of phases, important time points, and significant elements that make the story meaningful for the experiential intention. Likewise, the stories selected are turned into patterns that contain ‘experiential specifications’. In this step, it is recommended to use analogies of situations that capture the essence of the experience, and assign them an experiential theme that represents the core of the story.

In the following, this step is described for the anecdote that inspired the final design:

Figure 4. Anecdotes selected

‘Dissolving in the moment’ anecdote

My office has a special area where the coffee machine is placed. This space is full of colours and comfortable furniture and a really beautiful view over a park. I always go alone there once in a while to think and have some coffee. I feel completely relaxed. What I like the most is that it feels like I am not working anymore! (female participant, age 34)

This anecdote represents the cluster ‘positive emotions’. In practice, you may not like drinking coffee, and your routine when taking breaks at work may be different from the one described. However, you may recognize the feelings reported in it if you were to go through the same situation. Hassenzahl (2010) calls this the ‘plausibility’ and ‘resonance’ — feeling of recognition — of experiences. In this case, the participant who likes drinking her coffee in this sensorial place has the facilities to ‘let her mind wander’ and ‘dissolve in the moment’, which is the experiential theme assigned to the narrative as expressed in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Picture-metaphor ‘letting the mind wander’

The experience of ‘dissolving in the moment’ at the office starts with a decision to take a step away from your desk. One important canon of the moment is the fact that the person leaves the desk physically (leaving their work), but not the office. People do it with the intention of having a moment of privacy where they are somewhat distant but not isolated from the rest. Having an overview of the surroundings reinforces the feeling.

The experience is ignited by an ‘alibi’ (i.e. a coffee break) that defines the time frame of the experience and creates an explanation for the moment of seclusion (it justifies the action). The ‘space’ or ‘context’ where the experience takes place is inscribed inside certain physical boundaries. This context is a source of delight and pleasure (a treat). The reward is complete relaxation. This space is facilitated and encouraged by the company and it is highly sensorial and ‘beautiful’. The moment should not interfere with the working routine but rather let people choose the best moment to take action for themselves. There are three main phases: the person working, the decision to take action (alibi), and the event itself.

To summarize, the key elements of the experience are: the person has this experience alone and for his/her own pleasure

(self-indulgence); the experience can be a routine, but not too frequent; the environment becomes a treat; in this space the person can ‘let his mind wander’; there is a certain distance from the working desk; and there is an element (alibi) that justifies the action.

This narrative represents in a more formal and abstracted way the experience described in the story. Once the meaningful elements of the story are dissected and the experience is authored, the process of designing a product to mediate such an experience takes place.

Step 4. Conceptualization

The set of ‘experiential specifications’ described in the narrative form the basis for the conceptualization phase of the process and for the final design proposal. The experiential intention is the main guidance for the design process, and therefore all the elements of the experience ought to be considered. The experience is put to the fore and shaped by the material designed (Hassenzahl et al., 2013; Hassenzahl, 2013).

The design proposal that resulted in the design case was called *Gibbous Chair* (Figure 6). The *Gibbous Chair* is an elegant piece of furniture especially designed for the office environment as a resting chair. The chair provides the context to ‘let one’s mind wander’ and ‘dissolve in the moment’. This experiential intention is defined and mediated by a number of elements. The most apparent element is the pronounced height of the chair, which is as much as three times the height of a normal (office) chair. This new perspective of the environment becomes a treat for the office worker. Moreover, the elevation provides a moment of seclusion from the environment without being in isolation. The office worker enjoys this moment of pleasure in a semi-private way.

The second element that defines the experiential intention is the ‘alibi’ that explains and justifies the moment of pleasure. People need to have a reason to sit there, to be entitled to use it. The *Gibbous chair* provides them with two elements that justify their action: a magazine rack in which office workers share interesting things to read, and a coffee table. These elements aim to have the same effect as the coffee in the original story. The person prepares the coffee, and steps away from the desk in order to have a moment of seclusion. It is important to note that the *Gibbous Chair* is not intended to be used for work-related activities, and therefore it does not provide the space to do so. For that reason, the coffee table was designed to be too small to be used for work purposes. This connects to the experiential intention, since the moment of pleasure is experienced by stepping away from the desk, and by leaving your work behind for a moment. In *Gibbous Chair*, office workers find the facilities to enjoy a short moment of relaxation and self-indulgence.

Step 5. Evaluation

Generally, the result of a problem-driven design process, and the concept selection, can be evaluated taking into consideration the design specifications derived from the problem

Figure 6. The Gibbous Chair storyboard

statement, the accuracy to accomplish these, and the expectations of the clients. In the case of possibility-driven design there is no need to fulfil or any problem to address. How then can then the results be evaluated?

Usually, the experiential patterns guide the process to preliminary concept ideas. These concepts should be evaluated by considering how well the material recreates the experience targeted, as well as other (more) usual criteria like simplicity, aesthetics, and level of innovation. Moreover, the client and stakeholders should be involved in this process as in most product development cycles. However, since the result of these steps (the concept) embodies an experience, it is strongly suggested to use (experiential) prototypes to recreate the feelings. After all, evaluating (and judging) an experience should take place by ‘experiencing’ it in a real-life situation, in order to test whether its intended qualities are achieved.

In the design case, a prototype was built and tested in an office setting in order to learn from the experiences of people when the product was placed in their environment. Important findings include the positive perception of the design by most participants, and the rich and varied descriptions of their experiences while using the chair. Some described it as being on a different layer, as a new and fresh perspective, and even as a ski lift bringing you through the clouds.

DISCUSSION

The present paper suggests an approach to possibility-driven design as an alternative to traditional problem-driven design approaches. Note, however, that we do not intend to suggest that the traditional ways of designing should be substituted by a possibility-driven design view, nor do we devalue their results. Many of the problems faced by our modern societies, from hunger to lack of water supplies, need and must be addressed by the powerful tools of a problem-driven approach. Instead, we are proposing a view of design based on possibilities as an addition to current design practices — an addition that offers alternative results that might extend the solution space beyond merely reducing a deficiency.

The steps suggested in our approach parallel those of a classic problem-driven design cycle in that the process follows a linear sequence from an analysis phase to the evaluation of results. Indisputably, the starting point of both approaches is different — if not opposite. One focuses on undesirable aspects in a context, while the other concentrates on desirable aspects. One might wonder, however, if the difference lies only in how to frame the situation, or if it also exists in the design process itself and the steps to follow. In traditional problem-driven design cycles, product design specifications mostly guide the

design process after the analysis phase until the evaluation of the final concept (e.g. Pahl & Beitz, 1988; Roozenburg & Eekels, 1995; Ulrich & Eppinger, 1995). These specifications are generally measurable and comparable (e.g. the chair should accommodate users from P5-P90). In our approach, we suggest to have 'experiential specifications' to lead the design process, instead of solely technical ones. These specifications are to a great extent intangible. On the basis of this, we consider the approach to have indeed certain similar qualities compared to its traditional counterpart, but the focus on experiential product specifications differs greatly from guiding the process along more objective, clear-cut boundaries. This presents certain limitations of the approach. For instance, if you want to increase the efficiency of plane combustion engines, or prevent chemical reactions in intravenous medical devices, an approach focusing on positive experiences might not be as suitable as having a number of technical specifications that guide the process. Moreover, in our approach, personal anecdotes and user involvement was key to finding possibilities since, after all, it was about office workers' subjective well-being. The approach would fall short of tools if used in cases where user involvement is not considered, as might be the case in more utilitarian or industrial settings, i.e. designing new ways of making the process of injection moulding more reliable, or researching how chicken can easily find the food tray in poultry farms.

Our approach to design for possibilities used personal and autobiographical anecdotes as a source of inspiration. We then attempted to cluster them to select five for the design process. This raises an important question: how do we choose the best possibility and why? In the design case presented we decided to select the ones we considered were richer in terms of describing the situation. It was a rather subjective way to decide whether one possibility had more potential than another, and depended greatly on the design team and relevant stakeholders. However, having a clear goal and further specifications regarding the context and/or the users would likely facilitate the selection of possibilities. Specifications and demands can also facilitate the evaluation of the concepts in later stages of the design process.

The main suggestion underlying the approach described in this paper, and the related design case, is the idea that possibilities can be a valuable direction for design and that they can be designed (for). Problems bother us, and they are rendered negative and undesirable. Possibilities, on the other hand, are positive potentials. For the specific design case described, and, in general, for design approaches that aim at designing possibilities to increase happiness, considering theories and frameworks of positive psychology seemed relevant. The scientific study of subjective well-being already took on the challenge of studying the human potentials beyond neutrality. A mixed approach of both a top-down input, i.e. theories, as well as bottom-up insights, i.e. personal anecdotes, was used here. This implies that possible applications of a possibility-driven design approach can go beyond mere pleasure and self-indulgence, to designing for a meaningful, fulfilling, and happy life (see Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013). Possibilities can also

present themselves as solutions to problems. In the Eurostar project example, if supermodels were paid to serve train passengers, the problem of people wanting to be on time in Paris would have been solved by introducing something 'positive' that reframes the situation and takes away the undesirable aspects of it. Probably, people would take the train earlier, but perceive the trip as an enjoyable experience. In this case, instead of trying to reduce a deficiency, something positive is added that takes away the negative evaluation of the situation. Likewise, Gibbous Chair presents a positive experience by enabling office workers to have a moment of relaxation and self-indulgence that has been provided by the employer, a fact that can add significance to its user.

The result of the illustrative design case is a new product category — a chair with a different purpose compared to usual (office) chairs. Is radical innovation an implication of the approach? Or can it also be used for incremental innovation? One particularity of the design case presented in this paper was the conceptual freedom offered by the client and the explorative nature of the design brief. These elements, together with the experience methodology (Hassenzahl et al., 2013), steered the process to a novel purpose than what is normally conceived by a chair. However, designing for possibilities can also improve existing products and situations that are already around us (e.g. the Eurostar could have had a certain layout that allows for more interaction between passengers). We believe that embracing possibilities as a fuel for design can bring about improvements to existing products, i.e. incremental innovation, as well as possible changes of frame and meaning to new ones, i.e. radical innovation (see Norman & Verganti, 2014).

CONCLUSION

A possibility-oriented approach to design is not aiming to replace our common understanding of designing as a way of reducing deficiencies. The potential of this approach lies in appreciating both the implications for an alternative culture of innovation on the one hand, and the opportunity to design for a better future on the other — a future offering prospects and potentials. We hope to have shown through the design case that it is possible to design for possibilities, and that possibilities are there to be discovered. We believe that a possibility-oriented approach to design holds the potential of delivering products and technologies that will enable people to explore their capabilities in a more positive and humane way.

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CONSTRUCTION PARAMETERS FOR HYPERMEDIA COMICS TO LEARNING BASED ON THE GAMIFICATION CONCEPT

Raul Inácio Busarello, Luciane Maria Fadel, Vania Ribas Ulbricht
Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina, Brazil
✉ raulbusarello@gmail.com, liefadel@gmail.com, vrulbricht@gmail.com
Patricia Biegging
Universidade de São Paulo, Brazil
✉ pbiegging@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Starting from the construction of a hypermedia comics learning object, this article aims to clarify which gamification elements have been introduced in this artifact. Thus we discuss the relationship between features and elements that make up the games for the student's motivation, the aspects of storytelling games, and the language of comics. Besides the development of the learning objects we emphasize gamification topics used in comics. As a result we identify that many gamification elements contribute in order to make the artifact as emotional as possible. Topics such as fantasy help us to define the theme and genre of comics; clear goals, time and pressure, and feedback help in the dynamic of the students' test. The comics are structured on elements such as: onboarding, levels, challenges, as well as quests and progressive disclosure.

KEYWORDS: *gamification, comics, hypermedia, learning object, experience*

INTRODUCTION

Contemporary reality shows us that we need to adjust learning practices (Lazzarich, 2013), and invest in creative education based on society's current technology (Novaes, 2003). In the learning process it is necessary that teachers invest in extracurricular activities that encourage student participation (Tuncel and Alva, 2010), in order to stimulate student motivation and creativity, which in turn increases student performance, both academically and cognitively (Dias et al., 2004).

In this context we acknowledge the efficacy of storytelling in the learning process (Weller, 2000). However, we understand the development of a learning artifact based on hypermedia storytelling as a challenge, because it is necessary that we explore the nonlinearity possibilities together with characteristics of learning objects (Busarello, 2011).

In a nonlinear environment storytelling unfolds through fragments with connection points between each other, and allows the user to know a story apart from its conventional linearity (Murray, 2003; Steiner and Tomkins, 2010). This immersive aspect enables a more emotional and investigative navigation, facilitating the knowledge assimilation process by the user. It's because this aspects increases the user engage-

ment levels. Moreover, the storytelling in a hypermedia environment favors the three aesthetic categories that amplify user experiences: Immersion, Agency, and Transformation (Murray, 2003).

Based on guidelines of learning object construction (Macedo, 2010) we identified that the learning artifact must have addition to specific content, and must have some way to assess and monitor the student learning process. We emphasize that learning objects should have a clear and measurable goal, and it may be any media on digital or analog formats used for educational purposes. In that sense Busarello (2011) created a hypermedia learning object prototype based on comic language, focusing on learning the graphical representation concepts. This prototype was tested with a volunteer group who approved the effective use of comics for learning. The language of comics was selected because it helps to create an emotional connection with the students (Hughes and King, 2010; Eisner, 2008). Moreover, the structure formed by interconnected images in sequential frames enables greater integration of comics' content and the reader's imagination. It also enabled the readers to impose their individual reading pace, and therefore their personal learning pace (Gerde & Foster, 2008).

We verified, however, that despite hypermedia comics being effective tools for learning (Busarello, 2011), the concept of hypermedia comics covers a huge range of possibilities (McCloud, 2006) that promote the implementation of aesthetic resources (Murray, 2003), which can be deployed in many different ways through a story. We verified that these factors should be further explored alongside the construction of learning objects based on hypermedia comics. One hypothesis is that incorporating gamification concepts in hypermedia comics can contribute to an increase in student motivation through interaction with objects. Within this context, this article's objective is to explain which gamification elements are being introduced to construct learning through hypermedia comics, created by Busarello (2011).

This article is structured as four topics: the first one covers the characteristics and elements that make up the games and its relationship to the individual's motivation. The second topic discusses aspects of the game's storytelling and its relationship with the comic's storytelling. The third one presents the learning object development and the gamification topics and characteristics used by comics. The fourth topic is this article's concluding remarks.

MOTIVATION BY GAMIFICATION

The gamification's concept covers the game engine's uses for problem solving, motivation, and engagement for a given specific audience (Vianna et al., 2013). This approach confirms game thinking by using the systematic and mechanical act of playing in a context outside of the game. It is observed that individuals are motivated to play for four specific reasons: to gain mastery of a particular subject; to relieve stress; as entertainment; and as a means of socialization (Zichermann and Cunningham, 2011).

We understand that the difference between the actions within a game and the actions outside the game – the 'diffuse reality of life' – are differentiated by the feelings that individuals have. The first one of which there is a well-defined start and end, where the action rules are conscious and explicit and objects are clear (Collantes, 2013). Thus, the subject defines the actions with reference in the game's final goal. However in actions outside the game we observed that gamification could be applied to activities where it is necessary to stimulate the individual's behavior (Zichermann and Cunningham, 2011). The process of learning gamification can contribute to student motivation and the development of cognition (Schmitz et al., 2012).

Based on game mechanics, the concept of motivation is the articulation of an individual's experiences with the proposition of new perspectives 'internal and external of the redefinition processes, from the stimulus to creativity, autonomous thinking and providing welfare to the player' (Vianna et al., 2013, p.30, translation modified). As regards the factors that contribute to the individual's motivation, we identify the intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation. The first one

originates within the subject itself (Zichermann and Cunningham, 2011). Thus, the individual engages with things willingly because these things awaken interests, challenges, and engage, or give pleasure. The individual motivated in this way will seek news and entertainment, in order to satisfy their curiosity. Moreover, it has the opportunity to develop new skills and learn about something (Vianna et al., 2013). On the other hand, the extrinsic motivation is based on the world surrounding the individual (Zichermann & Cunningham, 2011). These motivations have as a starting point the subject's desire to obtain an external reward, such as social recognition and material goods (Vianna et al., 2013).

The challenge in creating environments that explore gamification is how to stimulate both forms of motivation in the person. We identify that certain extrinsic rewards can destroy intrinsic motivations that affect the motivational aspect of the individual. In the case of the person's action in an environment, for example, it is of utmost importance that the intrinsic motivations are preserved, otherwise the individual can simply leave this environment (Zichermann & Cunningham, 2011). The intrinsic behaviors are: 'mechanical', composed of the elements that enable the game to operate, as well as creating directions for the player's actions; 'dynamics', which are the interactions between player and game mechanics; and 'aesthetics', which determine how the game will make the player feel during the interaction.

Games' characteristics appropriation

The gamification's concept means to appropriate the most effective elements of a game — mechanics, dynamics, and aesthetics — to create and adapt the individual experiences in several fields (Vianna et al., 2013). Once maintained the subject's motivation should provide stimulus to individuals in high-quality and different formats (Li et al., 2012).

Among these stimuli various game elements of mechanics seek to interact with the individual emotionally (Zichermann and Cunningham, 2011). The following stand out:

1. Points: enables player monitoring during the interaction with the system. It can both serve as a stimulus for the player, and serve as a parameter so that the developer can read the results of individual performance.
2. Levels: steps that have the intention to indicate the progress of the player within the game.
3. Leaderboard: the purpose is to make simple comparisons, usually through ordered data such as names and scores.
4. Badges: records the goals of steady progress within the system. This topic encourages social promotion.
5. Onboarding: enables an inexperienced player to engage with the system. It indicates the development of player engagement to experience a game for the first time.
6. Challenges and Guests: these challenges for players demonstrate what to do within the game's universe.
7. Engagement loops: emotions that lead the player to re-engage in the experience of the game.
8. Customization: can be characterized in several ways, and enables the processing of system items by the player.

9. Feedback and Reinforcement: generally provide data to the players telling them about the environment and the result of their actions. Resources are essential to the game as a whole.

It is evident that among the characteristic elements of games, those that favor motivation stand out (Li et al., 2012). Fantasy makes for a more exciting experience for the individual, once he or she is embedded in the environment; objects and situations that are not present stimulate the player imagination. Clear goals enable the individual involvement in the system; once he or she objectively understands what must be done. Feedback and guidance enables immediate response by increasing the levels of the individual's engagement. It allows the individual to be conducted in the recovery of an error, if it occurs. Progressive disclosure favors the progressive increase of the user's knowledge while in the game it increases challenge levels. Time and pressure helps to set clear and challenging goals. Rewards allow the subject's performance to be measured by assigning scores after completion of a game level. Stimulus ensures high levels of engagement.

In the developing an artifact based on gamification it is necessary that it presents four essential characteristics (Vianna et al., 2013). The first is the goal of the object, the reason why an individual is performing that activity. It is the purpose designated for such an activity and one that the individual must constantly pursue; it is noted that the concept goes beyond target task completion. The second characteristic is the rules, whose function is to determine how the individual should behave and act towards challenges within a storytelling environment. The rules favor the release of creativity and strategic thinking, once they adjust the level of complexity of individual activities to be performed; the third one is the feedback system, where the individual has guidance about his or her position regarding the factors that regulate the interaction. The fourth is the voluntary participation, which states that the first three topics encourage person participation. We believe that other aspects of games – storytelling, interactivity, graphics support, rewards, competitiveness, virtual environment, among others – are constructed to create a close relationship with the goals, rules, feedback and voluntary participation (Vianna et al., 2013).

STORYTELLING EXPERIENCES: GAMIFICATION X COMICS

We understand that both the act of following a story or playing a game guarantee the individual a storytelling experience. It leads to cognitive experience, which translates into an emotional and sensory product of the individual when engaging in a structured and articulated life. However in the first case, the individual experiences a story where he/she is not included as a character. The individual participates 'live' in the story of another person, but without the possibility of interference in the plot course. In the second case, the individual 'lives' a story. In other words, the storytelling's development

depends on the person's active action for its resolution (Collantes, 2013). This experience feature of the individual in the games becomes an aesthetic category in hypermedia storytelling (Murray, 2003). The understanding is that the possibility found in immersive digital media contributes to building more participatory stories, once the viewer should actively act in the story course. In the case of hypermedia storytelling we identified that the viewer can experience a story in games (Murray, 2003; Brockmeier & Harré, 2003).

In the context of learning, agents present in some games such as character, competition, and game rules may have a direct effect on student development (Schimtz et al., 2012). Similarly, in a story construction these elements can be exploited in various ways. Any linear story covers a character performing actions somewhere, and these actions must respect the rules of the storytelling environment (Field, 2009). It's identified that in the immersion process the user is willing to obey the rules of that new universe, and this involves both aspects of navigation rules such as the story and competition (Murray, 2003).

For the game the storytelling unfolds through a hinged sequentiality of actions that determine the time, and lead to successive transpositions of situations and states (Collantes, 2013). This same characteristic sequential division is perceived in the most basic form of linear storytelling, with the classic division into three acts of a story: presentation, confrontation, and resolution (Field, 2009). The comic's fragmented structure in frames follows a sequential line that plays on the notions of time and space (Cirne, 2000). Also, in comics this sequentiality also allows a nonlinear story view (McCloud, 2006).

Comics are media that are able to create an emotional and physical connection with the reader by virtue of their own formatting in sequential images (Hughes & King, 2010). Used as a learning tool, comics can motivate students (Gerde & Foster, 2008; Iacono & Paula, 2011). Analogously games contribute to the motivation of individuals and therefore present themselves as an alternative in the learning process (Zichermann & Cunningham, 2011; Li et al., 2012). The gamification contributes to intensifying the experience of the subject, in order to arouse emotions (Vianna et al., 2013). We identify that one of the main characteristics of this media is the storytelling environment that exploits experiences in stories. These experiences are essential to constitute the memory, communication, and knowledge of individuals (Gordon, 2006).

GAMIFICATION THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF HYPERMEDIA COMICS

The learning objects are hypermedia comics that address the Solids concept of the Descriptive Geometry discipline. Basically through solid concepts the students seek to understand the geometric construction of objects represented by three dimensional-space. Based on Busarello (2011) the learning object is storytelling in comics with hypermedia navigation characteristics, with the nonlinear reading possibility be-

tween frame sets. It has links with access to the visualization of data and parallel stories, with the possibility of direct action from the reader, which leads to different story outcomes.

The Descriptive Geometry's contents are inserted as part of the fictional story, while the characters' actions are driven by readers who need the didactic knowledge to be able to interact and read the storytelling. The story theme was based on the humor and adventure genres. All the puzzles involve the solids discipline concept. This choice is based on the fantasy element of the game and seeks to encourage student motivation (Li et al., 2012).

The object's development is based on the proposed construction of learning objects where the nonlinear storytelling identifies that the user should have a single entry and exit of the object, but with several links within it (Nunes et al., 2011). The successful exit of the object is one that passes through the positive answer of the student during the final test. Moreover, the structure allows the user some freedom of choice however guided they are by the environment. Into it the interaction enables the user to feel in control of the story (Craveirinha & Roque, 2010).

As shown in Figure 1 each rectangle corresponds to a comic's page that supports one to three story frames. The arrows show the user's possible navigation. The rectangles in blue, where the description starts with the 'L' letter, represents the links' contents. These provide information about the solids' contents. It is possible to identify that in some parts the story

is divided – as in frames eleven, twelve, and thirteen. At this point the reader is able to follow a specific story character. It allows the reader to view the same subject through different points of view. Moreover it uses the aesthetic category of transformation (Murray, 2003) where the user has the ability to transform him or herself into a specific character. It also uses the Agency where the user action enables the choice of a specific path. In gamification the context of learning agents as character, competition, and game rules may have a direct effect on student development (Schimtz et al., 2012).

The knowledge tests within the object are used to monitor student learning, and are also a means of story navigation. Figure 1 shows that all tests lead to three possible paths. That's because when the test is submitted to the student, he or she should have to choose between three specific issues. If the student's answer is correct he or she is submitted to a story continuation. However if the answer is incorrect the characters are led to situations that induce the student to do the test again. To illustrate this process, the images below show the sequential pages corresponding to the first test's frames, 08, 09, 10.1, 10.2, and 10.3.

Figure 2 presents respectively the frames 08 and 09 (Figure 1). In the plot, the pirates arrive on an island that has a cottage, but while they moor up a sea monster attacks them. To escape, the characters run to enter the cottage. At this moment they need to decipher a puzzle to open the door. The puzzle is a test about a solid concept.

Figure 1. Structure of the Learning object in hypermedia comics

Figure 2. Comic fragments that lead to the test - Frames 08 and 09

Figure 3. Comic fragments in incorrect answer – Frames 10.1 and 10.3

If the student's answer was incorrect, one of the pirates fights the sea monster while the others try opening the door. Figure 3 presents respectively the story frames 10.1 and 10.3 (Figure 1). In the first one the pirate is struggling and those plot frames are the first wrong answer. Thus the student has the chance to do the exercise again. If the students answer the wrong option again, the comic's continuation shows the pirate being captured by the sea monster. These different outcomes are in agreement with other characteristic elements of games (Li et al., 2012):

- **Clear Goals:** once the student knows he/she has answered the test correctly the story proceeds;
- **Time Pressure:** once these goals defy the student and the unfolding of the story;
- **Feedback:** is related to the story continuation after the student answers. In those sequences, if the character is in a laughter situation the students know that the answer is wrong. Conversely, if the answer was correct the story continues its flow.

Figure 4 presents the frame 10.2 (Figure 1) that represents the image next to the correct answer. In it, the characters are safe inside the cottage. This frame does not present a possibility of returning to the test and the student should continue forward.

Figure 4. Comic fragments in correct answer – Frame 10.2

In Figure 1 we can see that the comic's beginning covers more stories and links for learning. It is based on the element of game mechanics onboarding that introduces the student to the storytelling and will also present the rules of the object gradually (Zichermann & Cunningham, 2011). Similarly the object is composed of five different tests divided into three learning levels, characterized by levels, quests, and challenges, as well as progressive disclosure of the object content (Li et al., 2012). While the students are learning the content, the test becomes more complex. The three comic Levels are: the pirates' journey to the island; the decision of what path each pirate must follow alone; and the final test where they meet up again to find the treasure chest. This distribution regards the division of a linear storytelling (Field, 2009), where the first level is the presentation, the second level the confrontation, and the third the story's resolution.

We believe that the challenges in the plot contribute to increase in individual immersion in the plot (Murray, 2013), as well as student engagement levels (Zichermann & Cunningham, 2011). Gamification aspects that can be incorporated into learning objects are: experience repetition, different possible paths, recognition and reward (Simões et al., 2013). The first and the second one are identified by the nonlinearity's possibilities into the story. The links associated with the story contents favor the repetition of experience, which is further stressed by tests. Analogously the path possibilities are explicitly identified in the plot parallel stories – between 10.2 and 14 frames – and the nonlinear navigation characteristics. The reward is identified in the continuity of reading at the end of each activity and completion of the story.

Based on the essential features of games (Vianna et al., 2013) the learning object presents a clear goal that is the learning of a solid discipline concept. The actions taken by the student during the storytelling course — story reading, educational content, resolution tests — are goals to be achieved by the individual. The rules are presented through browsing, where the student may choose to see the plot pictures or links and follow the paths of each character. Moreover, the student understands that the answers of tests have a direct effect on the story course. However there are the possibilities of the stu-

dents learning from their mistake and doing the tests again. This topic corroborates the feedback system where the story is used as media to motivate the learning of content. Thus, the feedback of answers leads the student to reading specific continuities in the plot. For example, when an answer is wrong the continuity of reading leads to an unfavorable outcome within history. But if it is correct the story continues. It enables the construction of a single story to each student (Murray, 2003), and consequently affects the learning process. In regards to the voluntary participation, we observed that the use of storytelling comics is a motivating factor in the learning process for students (Gerde & Foster, 2008; Short & Reeves, 2009; Hughes & King, 2010; Busarello, 2011). In the case of our hypermedia comics, the story assists in interpretation and exemplification of content that can seem abstract to students.

FINAL THOUGHTS

This article's objective was to clarify how gamification elements should be introduced in the construction of hypermedia comics for learning. We identified that in storytelling learning, artifact's construction requires the investment in characters and plots that emotionally captivate the student. In regards to the learning object we identified that the descriptive geometry content must be present in the obstacles encountered by the characters, and it should be explored by students during media's nonlinear navigation. The navigation mechanism is tied to the knowledge that the student acquires during reading the story, where the users' shares are parameters for the construction of its own storytelling version. Thus, links enable the student to know more about the learning content or the story. While, the way to assess the student's knowledge must be embedded in the story frames and as part of the plot. A given obstacle that the character must have to overcome is present in this form of test, and it requires the learning student's knowledge. The test's answer feedback determines the story's continuation. The student will know the right or wrong answer depending on the character action in a certain set of frames after the test.

The possibilities in the hypermedia comic's construction favor the concepts of gamification uses, both as student's motivation and for the mechanical's construction of artifact. Construction elements such as fantasy help to define the story theme and genre; clear goals, time and pressure and feedback assist in dynamic assessments that students must do in the course of reading and navigation. The comics are structured based on elements of game mechanics. For example, onboarding, levels, challenges and quests, progressive disclosure, experimentation repetition, and opportunities and reward pathways are used for the characteristic elements of the learning object.

Finally the hypermedia comics learning object presents essential gaming features, such as goals which are linked to learning, rules which structure the way a student interacts with the story and the environment, and system feedback,

which is mainly related to the reviews during reading and the story's sequence after the tests. We believe that these elements may contribute to the student's voluntary participation in the learning.

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THE INFLUENCE OF COLOR IN FRAGRANCE PERCEPTION

DESIGNING PACKAGINGS FOR PERFUMES

Camila Assis Peres Silva, Clíce Sanjar Mazzilli
 University of São Paulo
 ✉ camila.assis@usp.br, clíce@usp.br

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a discussion about the importance of the use of colors in a packaging design for perfumes. Facing the potentiality of such visual stimuli in optimizing the user experience in the moment of choosing and buying. In this paper we point out the particularities of a packaging design for a product such as perfume. We discuss the use of verbal metaphor to describe fragrances, and we also discuss the possibility of associating smells and colors through such metaphors. Materials, methods, and the results of a survey with Brazilian consumers are presented here. The results were compared with the fragrance market practices, and lead us to conclude that certain colors better reflect the message of a fragrance. We argue, therefore, that once using the appropriate colors in packaging design, the communication can be enhanced, and the perception of the quality of a perfume can be anticipated even before it is smelt.

KEYWORDS: *packaging design, color, perfume, consumer perception, Brazil.*

INTRODUCTION

Packaging plays an important role for the perfumery industry and market. The visual communication applied to a packaging design may increase its influence over the consumer. We argue that, among other factors, the color of packaging has influence over fragrance perception. Before discussing this factor, we will conduct a brief introduction about the particularities of designing packaging for perfumes.

Packaging is as important as the perfume it contains. Unlike other kinds of packaging, which in their origin were more concerned with the strength and capacity of storage, the packaging used to protect and store the perfumes have been treated for centuries with the care given to an object of art. By analyzing the perfumery history, we can see that the perfume was for many years exclusive to the nobility (Silva, 2012). As a luxury item, the packaging of perfumes also carried the trappings of an object worthy of the nobility. The finest materials and techniques were used, varying according to the historical moment of each culture. Today, perfume is available to the masses. In spite of this, the primacy of beauty still remains in the design for perfume packaging. Throughout perfume's trajectory in society, many changes have occurred in the social, economic, political, technological, and environmental

spheres. Two events, though, have affected the paradigms of packaging design: the industrial revolution and the system of sales in large retail.

With the advent of industrialization, coupled with mass consumption of perfumes, manufacturers were faced with the possibility of producing packaging in a fast and economical way so as to meet the growing market. For many years, extraordinary artisans were in charge of packaging design for perfumes (Mariacher, 1992). However, with industrialization, the packaging production passes into the hands of a large team. Engineers, technicians, machine operators, marketing professionals, and designers all play a role in this chain of production. The implementation of self-service in the mid-twentieth century (Camargo & Negrão, 2008) is a second milestone in the production of packaging. The emergence of retail trade and supermarkets modifies the dynamics of sales. No more are those sellers behind the counter, listening and answering every consumer's doubts and appeals. Packaging will be responsible for providing the necessary information concerning technical, regulatory, and commercial issues. It should also be attractive and compelling; it needs to be self salable. As packaging specialists usually say, packaging is now playing the role of a 'silent salesman' (Pilditch, 1961). Such changes in the production and in the system of

sales have been demanding new skills and knowledge. The designer should comprehend the limitations of industrial production so as to take advantage of it. In this way they can design packaging, which will make a difference to both the company and the consumer.

Among the different approaches that can be woven around a packaging design, we chose to analyze, in this paper, the influence of visual communication elements in the packaging for perfumes; and, more specifically, the usage of colors for communicating the characteristics of each one of the fragrances. In a project of this nature, where what has been selling is the fragrance with its promises of welfare, seduction, and freshness (Ashcar, 2011), packaging must communicate such attributes. We therefore believe that the visual elements such as shape, texture, and color must be consistent with the stimuli that the fragrance will supposedly trigger in the consumer. Given the power of colors to affect people, proven by its extensive use in communication, we decided to focus this investigation on them. Could colors represent the smells?

Scientists have proven that to visually identify a smell is not an easy task, because olfactory perceptions vary from individual to individual (Wolfe et al., 2012). Nevertheless, research in the field of neuroscience in different countries has shown positive results that point to a cross-modal association among the different senses. Encouraged by this, we decided to investigate possible associations between colors and smells in the Brazilian market. As such, this study aims to present results and reflections about the perception of a group of consumers. Despite perceptions being particular to each individual, there is indeed a trend of certain associations between colors and smells.

THE OLFATORY MESSAGE TRANSLATED INTO VISUAL AND VERBAL LANGUAGE

Communication in the world has been long dominated by verbal language, that is, by speech. Certainly, our body language is the most immediate way to express feelings. It is linked to instincts and involuntary responses in our body. However, expressing feelings is different from communicating feelings. When the intention is to share with our peers what we are feeling, we frequently use words to do it. In what concerns smells, we can react to an odor only by facial expression. But to share this feeling with someone else requires a little more information. Considering that humans have difficulty in verbalizing a smell and that the ability to discriminate between them varies according to a range of facts such as gender, age, and experience (Wolfe et al., 2012), to communicate an olfactory perception is not an easy task. 'When one tries to describe the smell elicited by a rose, for example, it will require multiple words, representing feelings, emotions, or memories of the individual' (Teixeira et al., 2013, p.97). Because of this, we can have different interpretations about the same smells. Indeed, the complexity of the olfactory system creates difficulty to have a unique definition for each odor. The

perfumery industry, though, has invested in building a vocabulary to facilitate identification and discrimination of odors (Teixeira et al., 2013; Zarzo & Stanton, 2009; Donna, 2009).

Given the extensive range of ingredients available in the world of perfumery, it is a common market practice to classify fragrances in olfactory families. This classification can vary from company to company, although highly trained specialists have done it. Despite being largely classified by empirical methods, recently, perfumes can be classified by technological processes such as the 'Perfumery Radar methodology', which consists of a software tool developed by a group of engineers with the purpose of 'reducing the arbitrariness to the empirical classification' (Teixeira et al., 2013, p.113). For this research, however, we have opted for the classification presented by the digital magazine *Osmoz* (Table one), elaborated by the Firmenich fragrance company. Even though it is an empirical classification, it is a recognized reference in the perfumery market. Moreover, *Osmoz* presents an approach that comes from meeting with the goal of this research. The magazine presents a definition for each one of the olfactory families (Table 1). In doing so, the consumer can have an idea of the feelings each family may elicit.

Just as people use words to describe smells, we know that in the field of visual language qualities are also assigned to colors. In the case of colors, we have the universal classification of warm and cold colors, which is a reflection of people's experience in daily life. The fire, which makes us feel warm, usually varies from yellow to red (warm colors). The ice, which makes us feel cold, is the water in a solid stage. The water in its turn is seen as blue (cold color) when in a higher concentration. However we have been giving meanings to the colors which are much more abstract than this. Studies of Goethe (2013), Kandinsky (2000), and Farina (1986) show an attempt at translating colors into sensations; that is, an attempt to describe the psychological effects of colors on people.

Given the predominance of the verbal language in our societies, we can infer that the use of verbal metaphors is a natural attitude when people want to express feelings. If the words are capable of translating odors and visual stimuli, it means that in some way we can connect these feelings to words. Especially if we assume that all the senses are connected. In other words, if we consider that there are not 'departmentalized senses, but synesthesias as interrelationship of all the senses' (Plaza, 1987, p.46). From that thought, we decided to conduct consumer research using verbal language as a connection to the possible association between colors and smells.

COULD THE COLORS REPRESENT THE SMELLS?

It is common sense that colors are an important element in communicating emotions. Miguel Teixeira and his colleagues (Teixeira et al., 2013, p.99) assume that the look of a perfume (including its colors) greatly influences its judgment. They argue that the process of fragrance perception is hierarchical (Figure 1). It is initially influenced by culture, memories, and

OLFACTORY FAMILIES	DEFINITIONS/ ATTRIBUTES
Oriental (Men)	Refreshed by aromatic or citrus facets, oriental compositions draw their richness and sophistication from precious substances such as amber, resin, tobacco, spices, exotic woods, and animal notes.
Oriental (Women)	Orientials —also known as 'amber' fragrances — stand out because of their unique blend of warmth and sensuality. They draw their richness from heady substances like musk, vanilla, and precious woods that are often associated with exotic floral and spicy scents.
Citrus(Men)	This family includes all perfumes mainly composed of citrus notes such as bergamot, lemon, orange, tangerine, and grapefruit. These fragrances are characterized by their freshness and lightness. The first 'Eaux de Cologne' belongs to this category. The masculine character comes from the frequently strong presence of aromatic and spicy notes.
Citrus(Women)	Each perfume in this family is primarily composed of citrus scents such as bergamot, lemon, orange, tangerine, and grapefruit, to which other orange-tree elements (orange blossoms, petit grain, or neroli oil) have been added. Floral or even chypre accords are sometimes present as well. These perfumes are characterized by their freshness and lightness including the first 'Eaux de Cologne'.
Woody	These perfumes, with their woody middle note, are warm and opulent when based on sandalwood or patchouli. Cedar and vetiver make them dryer. These warm, dry, and elegant masculine accords often contain a dash of citrus or aromatic notes.
Floral	This family is composed of a large variety of creations ranging from sumptuous bouquet arrangements to 'soli flora' compositions. Perfumers can let their creativity run wild, enriching florals with green, aldehydic, fruity, or spicy hints. With its natural scent, the floral note is one of the most widely used in women's perfumes.
Aromatic	Aromatic notes are mainly composed of sage, rosemary, thyme, and lavender usually complemented with citrus and spicy notes. These compositions' manly character makes them an all-time favorite in men's perfumery.
Chypre	Chypre by Coty enjoyed such success in 1917 that 'chypre' is now a generic name for a whole category of timeless, classic perfumes. The compositions are based on oak moss, ciste-labdanum, patchouli and bergamot accords. The richness of chypre notes mixes wonderfully with fruity or floral notes. This family is made up of distinguished, instantly recognizable fragrances.

Table 1. Characteristics of some olfactory families. Source: Osmoz magazine. (2013).

Figure 1. The pyramid of scent perception based on Teixeira et al. (2013, p.99).

Figure 2. Fragrance wheel by Michael Edwards, from *Fragrances of the World* website.

past experiences. Then, in a second stage, we have the influence of the other sensory stimuli such as sight, taste, hearing, and touch. Based on this, we can infer that colors can represent smells.

Besides this, we could observe, by analyzing the perfumery segment, the trend of using colors so as representing smells. The fragrance wheel created by the fragrance expert Michael Edwards (Figure 2) is an example of this. In a quick search on the Internet we can find lots of attempts of fragrance classification by a colorful wheel. Moreover, some research has been undertaken both in the cosmetics segment (Kim, 2009; Milotic, 2006) and in the drinks (Gilbert et al., 1996; Morean, 2011; Morrot et al., 2001) with the objective of identifying such associations. Despite the peculiarities of olfactory perception (factors such as age and sex have influence over it) the results show that the colors can influence odors. Based on this, we decided to investigate the Brazilian market by opposing consumer opinion to market practice.

Materials and methods

We elaborated an online survey in order to investigate how consumers react to the names of olfactory families and also the characteristics attributed to them. Through this approach we aim to investigate how familiar with the perfumery vocabulary the consumers were. Moreover, we aim to identify if the associations which consumers make between color and smells are similar to those we can find in the market. The online survey was elaborated in Google Drive tool and it was distributed through the social network of the authors, mostly composed of designers and design students. However, the professional occupation was not an issue of selection. Respondents were encouraged to spread the survey to their re-

spective social networks. Only personal information, such as age, gender, and city of residence were collected. In a period of one month (from 11/17/2013 to 12/13/2013), we obtained a total of 159 respondents (106 women and 53 men). The majority of respondents (80%) were under 35, and over 90% were residents from the Southeast region.

Respondents were not asked about their habits of consumption of perfumes. They were only asked to freely associate words (olfactory family names and their attributes) to one or more colors. We opted to use a qualitative approach and employed open-ended questions in order to avoid influence over the respondents. For this survey we selected the most known families of fragrances in the Brazilian market: citrus, floral, woody, and oriental. For each one of these families, we chose two words that according to the perfumery literature better represent the emotion elicited by them (see Table 1). For Citrus we have the qualities of *freshness* and *lightness*. Based on the floral olfactory family speech we could infer the qualities of *romantic* and *feminine*. With regard to the woody family we selected the qualities *warm* and *elegant*. Finally for the oriental family we selected the qualities of *sophistication* (*richness*) and *sensuality*. It is important to highlight that respondents were not informed that those qualities had a connection with the olfactory families presented. Moreover, the four qualities were presented in a different order to the olfactory families.

Two questions were posed to the consumers. Each one of them was divided into four sub questions (four attributes and four olfactory families). The first question posed was 'What color or colors do you associate with perfumes which have the following characteristics?'. This question was followed by an example: 'Blue, light blue, silver, gold, dark green... You can inform the color and the tone that you feel is most appropriate'. Then the four sub questions were presented:¹ (1) *Freshness and lightness*, (2) *Sophistication and sensuality*, (3) *Warm and elegant*, (4) *Romantic and feminine*. The second question presented was 'What color or colors do you associate with perfumes which belong to the following olfactory families?'. The same example given in the first question was given in this second one. The sub questions presented were: (1) *Citrus Perfume*, (2) *Woody Perfume*, (3) *Floral Perfume*, (4) *Oriental Perfume*. In doing so, our aim was to identify if the colors mentioned for each olfactory family would coincide with those colors indicated for the characteristics associated to each one of these families. That is, if the colors displayed for citrus perfume were similar to the colors indicated for the attributes of *freshness* and *lightness*.

Results

The table bellow summarizes the results obtained from the research. As mentioned before, consumers were free to give the answers to the questions. As a result of this, we got a va-

¹ In the original language (Portuguese) the qualities presented were: (1) *Frescor e Leveza*, (2) *Sofisticação e Sensualidade*, (3) *Quente e Elegante*, (4) *Romântico e feminino*.

	CITRUS	FRESHNESS AND LIGHTNESS
TOTAL OF MENTIONED COLORS	208 (100%)	223 (100%)
1st most mentioned color	Green - 88 (42%)	Green - 81 (36.3%)
2nd most mentioned color	Yellow - 50 (24%)	Blue - 75 (33.6%)
3rd most mentioned color	Orange - 48 (23%)	Lilac - 12 (5.4%) Yellow - 12 (5.4%)
	Woody	Warm and elegant
Total of mentioned colors	190 (100%)	217 (100%)
1st most mentioned color	Brown - 98 (51.6%)	Red - 83 (38.2%)
2nd most mentioned color	Yellow - 16 (8.4%)	Orange - 29 (13.4%)
3rd most mentioned color	Green - 13 (6.8%)	Golden - 24 (11%)
	Floral	Romantic and feminine
Total of mentioned colors	226 (100%)	219 (100%)
1st most mentioned color	Pink - 103 (45.6%)	Pink - 128 (58.4%)
2nd most mentioned color	Purple/ lilac - 35 (15.5%)	Purple/ lilac - 24 (10.9%)
3rd most mentioned color	Yellow - 26 (11.5%)	Red - 17 (7.8%)
	Oriental	Sophistication and sensuality
Total of mentioned colors	198 (100%)	229 (100%)
1st most mentioned color	Red - 63 (31.8%)	Red - 69 (30%)
2nd most mentioned color	Yellow - 21 (10.6%)	Golden - 38 (16.6%)
3rd most mentioned color	White - 18 (9%)	Purple/ lilac - 31 (13.5%)

Table 2. Results of consumer research. Source: Created by the authors.

riety of nomenclatures. Light green, dark green, royal blue, bright red, sunset red, ice, amber, crystal white, old rose, burned rose, tropical colors: just to give some examples. We considered, though, in a single group the different variations of tones from light to dark from the same hue. That is, when we mention yellow we refer to the different yellows informed by the consumers.

Analyzing the results shown in Table 2, and comparing it with the fragrance wheel (Figure 3), we can identify correlations between consumers' opinions and the colors chosen by Michael Edwards to represent such fragrances. The citrus family is represented in the fragrance wheel by the color yellow, the second most mentioned by the respondents. For the floral family, the fragrance wheel presents three variations. Selecting only the floral and soft floral (excluding floral oriental because it merges floral with another family, the oriental) we can see that the pink and red colors are used, as mentioned by the respondents. With regard to the woody family, the wheel presents the use of yellowish brown and tones of green, again according to the responses obtained in the survey. Finally, in the oriental family we have the use of a rosy red tone. From this first analysis we can infer that, even though the perceptions vary from person to person, some colors can be associated with the smells. In order to investigate the correspondences between colors and smells, we proceed to the analysis comparing the associations revealed in the survey answers (characteristics and olfactory families) with the market practices. For this purpose we selected some packag-

Figure 3. Citrus, floral, woody, oriental: the colors of the families according to Michael Edwards.

ing of Brazilian perfumes, which are classified in the citrus, floral, woody, and oriental families.

Looking at the table with the results it is interesting to observe the influence of raw material on the association of col-

ors and smells. In the citrus family, the three most mentioned colors are the same we can find in the fruits used as raw material for this kind of fragrance, such as lemon, orange, bergamot, and mandarine. Besides that, over 60% of the listed colors were green and yellow as seen in the packaging of perfumes from the *Natura* company for citrus fragrances (Figure 4). It is worth highlighting that the colors yellow and green are also mentioned for the attributes used for citrus fragrances. The color blue, the second most mentioned as the color for the attributes of freshness and lightness, almost had the same amount of indications as the color green. Blue is a color universally used to represent the cold. In addition to this, we can notice that *Natura* also uses the color blue for a citrus fragrance. Moreover, we argue that the colors presented in open-air natural spaces may influence the perception of freshness: the colors of forest (green) and of the ocean (blue), the grass (green), and the sky (blue).

As for the floral family, the most mentioned colors were pink and purple/lilac, totaling more than 60%, probably because these colors are commonly found in flowers. In addition to this, it is very common to find perfumes from floral olfactory families using these kinds of colors. If we take a look at some of the packaging of *Natura's* perfumes, we can confirm this tendency (Figure 5). When consumers were asked to indicate

colors related to the attributes of their family (*romantic and feminine*), again they mentioned pink and purple/lilac. The color red was also mentioned. Once again we can notice a connection here between scents, words, and colors. Because flowers and romanticism are connected in the collective imaginary of people's daily life, the results could not be different. In a quick search on the Internet we can find flowers as a symbolism of women and romance. Furthermore, 'the floral note is one of the most widely used in women's perfumes' (see Table 1).

With regard to the woody olfactory family, brown and its variations were mentioned in more than 50% of responses. Brown is the color of the wood, so that was a natural association to be made. We believe that, because they were not submitted to olfactory stimulus, the consumers made a connection with what they consider as raw material for the fragrances of the woody family; that is, the tree. Consequently they also mentioned other colors related to trees: yellow and green (leaves and twigs). As for the colors mentioned to the attributes of warm and elegant, even though they were not the same ones indicated to the woody family, we can establish a kind of connection among the responses. The color brown can easily vary to tones of yellow, oranges and reds. In this sense, all the responses have a connection. Brown, yellow, orange,

Figure 4. Citrus fragrances from the *Natura* company.

Figure 5. Floral fragrances from the *Natura* company

Figure 6. Woody fragrances from the *Natura* company

Figure 7. Oriental fragrances from the *O Boticário* company

red: they are all warm colors. Analyzing the packaging of perfumes of the *Natura* company, we can see the use of the colors mentioned by the respondents (Figure 6).

Finally, it was in the oriental family that we could observe more variation in the results. We did not have a strong indication for just one or two colors. If we consider the most mentioned color, the oriental family was the one that had less votes, 31.8% for the color red. For citrus we have the first mentioned color (green) concentrating 42% of the votes. In the floral, we have 45.6% concentrated in the color pink. In the woody family, we have 51.6% concentrated in the color brown. In spite of this, and taking account the three most mentioned colors, there is a predominance of warm colors. This has everything to do with the definition presented for this olfactory family, as shown in Table 1. Furthermore, the yellow is the color of one of the main ingredients of this olfactory family: the vanilla ingredient. We can observe it in almost every perfume which has vanilla in its composition. They commonly have a liquid with a yellowish color, which influences the packaging when the bottle is transparent. This is, the liquid gives to the packaging a yellowish color².

Despite warm colors being the most mentioned in the oriental family, the colors white (seventeen mentions), and blue (thirteen mentions) were also regarded as representative. That is probably due to the reference these respondents may have from the Orient. Colors like blue and white are quite common in Asian landscapes. White and blue can be found in some packaging, however oriental fragrances usually have warm colors. It can be confirmed by checking the perfumes of the oriental family on the *Osmoz* magazine website. Lastly, regarding the colors mentioned for the attributes of *sophistication* and *sensuality*, we had the colors red and golden. These two colors are linked to the colors mentioned in the oriental family. However the third most mentioned color was purple/lilac, which is not as warm as red and yellow, but it is a color related to the royalty (Heller, 2013. p.196), and consequently with the idea of sophistication. It is not a warm color but it is also not a baseless choice, because we can find this kind of color in the packaging of oriental perfume from the *O Boticário* collection (Figure 7).

² In the website *Osmoz* (<http://www.osmoz.com>) we can find some examples of perfumes with vanilla. For instance we have *1881 en fleurs* (by Cerruti), *Aimez-moi* (by Caron), *Alchimie* (by Rochas), *Alien Essence Absolue* (by Thierry Mugler), and *Allure* (by Chanel).

CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

We live in an age where much of the attention, if not all, has converged on the consumer. One speaks about the power of influence of the consumers, the strength of collectiveness. One speaks of the importance of user experience, interactivity, and interface usability. It is worth highlighting that most of the time such experience begins at the point of sale, during the moment of the buying decision. The packaging in this sense plays an important role in the experience of the user/consumer. A packaging with inefficient visual communication runs the risk of being deprecated in the midst of competition. Packaging which does not appear in accordance with the content may generate frustration in the user. Moreover, in what concerns the packaging of perfumes, we argue that the more consonant with the perfume the visual communication is, the more successful the packaging will be. We assume that a visual language in synchrony with the smell will enhance the reception of the message you wish to convey.

In this paper we presented an investigation about the use of the colors to represent smells. From the results obtained through the survey we could conclude that consumers' associations between smells and colors are in consonance with what we can see in the market practice. We assume that it is a subject that requires thorough research. However, these initial results lead us to conclude that color perception can be linked to the olfactory perception. Even though each person has a particular perception, influenced by his own experience, social life also influences the way consumers perceive colors and smells. We believe that the better designers can understand the perception of consumers, the better and more efficiently they can design. As possibilities for future studies we point to the analysis of other visual elements such as shapes, typography, and textures. As well as research about the influence of colors over other fragrant products like shampoos, and air fresheners. In addition to this, we recommend other color perception surveys in which consumers are subjected to fragrance tests.

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UNIFIED USER EXPERIENCE MODEL ENABLING A MORE COMPREHENSIVE UNDERSTANDING OF EMOTIONAL EXPERIENCE DESIGN

Constantin von Saucken, Rafael Gomez
Technische Universität München, Queensland University of Technology
✉ saucken@pe.mw.tum.de, r.gomez@qut.edu.au

ABSTRACT

Design deals with improving the lives of people. As such interactions with products, interfaces, and systems should facilitate not only usable and practical concerns but also mediate emotionally meaningful experiences. This paper presents an integrated and comprehensive model of experience, labeled 'Unified User Experience Model', covering the most prominent perspectives from across the design field. It is intended to support designers from different disciplines to consider the complexity of user experience. The vision of the model is to support both the analysis of existing products, interfaces, and systems, as well as the development of new designs that take into account this complexity. In essence, we hope the model can enable designers to develop more marketable, appropriate, and enhanced products to improve experiences and ultimately the lives of people.

KEYWORDS: *Emotional Design, User Experience, UX, Unified User Experience Model*

INTRODUCTION

At its core the field of design is about creating a better life for people. As such interactions with products, devices, and interfaces should facilitate and mediate emotionally meaningful experiences so as to positively impact people's lives. User experience (UX) is understood in different ways by several disciplines (Roto et al. 2011); however there are common fundamental principles. Beyond usability, a point of interest in science and industry for many years, the recent approach of UX extends the view on user product interaction to include aspects of emotions (Green & Jordan, 2002; Hummels, 2000; Manzari, 2003). Therefore, the motivation of UX is about enhancing the overall experience to meet psychological and emotional needs, including the motives of the user (Hassenzahl, 2010). Further, by triggering the user's emotions it is more likely that this will increase brand loyalty and help create a point of difference for products in saturated markets.

The Complexity of Experiences

Experiences are situated in real life and need to be considered from this perspective, and due to their nature are complex, contextual, evolving, dynamic, short and long-term, and deal with the issue of time. It is relevant therefore that any conceptual model takes into account these aspects and attempts to acknowledge the complexity of UX.

In this paper we propose an integrated and comprehensive model of experience covering the most prominent perspec-

tives from across the design field. It is intended to support designers from different disciplines to consider and deal with the user experience. The vision is for the model, labeled 'Unified User Experience Model', to support both the analysis of existing products, interfaces, and systems as well as the development of new designs that take into account this complexity. In essence we hope the model can enable designers to develop more marketable, appropriate and enhanced products, and systems to improve experiences and ultimately the lives of people.

STATE OF THE ART

In order to develop an integrated model on UX we need to provide an overview on the state of the art models on user experience and emotional design. We divide them into two categories: models describing individual UX aspects and foundational principles (Norman, 2004; Desmet, 2002; Desmet & Hekkert, 2007; Jordan, 2000; Hassenzahl, 2010), and others describing UX as a process which includes multiple influences and is inherently more complex (Khalid & Helander, 2008; Karapanos et al., 2009; von Saucken et al., 2012; von Saucken et al., 2013b; Gomez, 2012; Gomez et al., 2013). Furthermore, we divide UX into a Micro and Macro perspective, which includes aspects from most of the models presented and contextualizes the user experience as a dynamic activity. Finally, we derive a unified approach that covers the relevant and important aspects for experience design synthesis.

Models Describing Fundamental UX Aspects

Presented here are prominent models on user experience and emotional design, including Norman's (2004) *Three levels of processing*, Desmet's (2002) *Basic model of product emotion*, Desmet & Hekkert's (2007) *Framework of product experience*, Jordan's (2000) *Four pleasures framework*, and Hassenzahl's (2012) *Three level hierarchy of goals*. They all focus on individual experience aspects and do not claim to regard UX holistically. This way, they are descriptive and support the foundational aspects of UX.

Processing Experiences by Norman (2004)

Norman (2004) details distinctive processing layers that cause different kinds of experiences including *visceral*, *behavioral*, and *reflective*. Norman posits that a product is perceived and automatically assessed through its look and feel (visceral), as well as its purpose and functionality (behavioral), leading to an action. Above these, the reflective level represents conscious thought and reflection of that experience (Figure 1).

- **Visceral level.** This is the fastest system of processing and makes rapid judgments and assessments of the perceived appearance and beauty of objects and the environment. Visceral design may relate to the shape, materials, colors, feel, sound, and smell of a product: the embodied design.
- **Behavioral level.** Deals with pleasure and effectiveness of use related to usability and functionality: What does a product do? What function does it perform? For experienced users this level of processing is performed almost unconsciously.
- **Reflective level.** When it comes to rationalizing the product interaction, it is the reflective level that is being engaged. Users think consciously about their products — about their stories, self-image, and pride. This processing is not aroused directly by sensory input, but is based on the memory of behavioral experience, and is highly dependent on the user's unique background (culture, values) and history (remembrance of experiences).

Figure 1. Three levels of processing by Norman (2004)

Product Emotions by Desmet (2002)

One of the earliest emotional experience models was the *Basic Model of Product Emotions* by Desmet (2002), consisting of four parameters in the eliciting process of emotions including appraisal, concern, product, and emotion (figure 2).

This model is based on the proposition that all emotional reactions result from a process in which individuals appraise the product as harmful or beneficial (Frijda, 1986). 'Appraisal' refers to the immediate and automatic evaluation of an event in which both individual concern and product interaction have an impact. 'Concern' relates to the significance or value that an individual places on any given experience. According to Frijda (1986), events that satisfy a concern yield positive emotions, while events that threaten a concern lead to negative emotions. The 'product' is the mediator and influences the overall appraisal by facilitating or threatening a concern. Desmet argues that the dynamic of all three parameters; appraisal, concern, and product, lead to an *emotional* reaction.

Product Experience Patterns by Desmet and Hekkert (2007)

With their *Framework of Product Experience*, Desmet & Hekkert (2007) present three different experience patterns that help designers 'design for experience'. They distinguish between aesthetic experience, experience of meaning, and the emotional experience attributed to a user-product interaction (Figure 3).

The 'aesthetic experience' pattern is triggered by the product's sensory impact on the user — the perceptual process. A product can be pleasant in terms of optic (beautiful to look at), acoustic (pleasant sound), haptic (good to touch), or olfactory (smells nice). The pattern relating to the subjective user's interpretation, labeled 'experience of meaning' pattern is based on memory retrieval and association of a product — the cognitive process. The experience of meaning depends on the individual and the cultural context of the user. When it comes to evaluation (appraisal) of product perception and cognition, an *emotional* experience can be triggered — an affective phenomenon.

Figure 2. Basic model of product emotions by Desmet (2002)

Figure 3. Framework of Product Experience by Desmet & Hekkert (2007)

Four Pleasures by Jordan (2000)

In *Designing Pleasurable Products*, Jordan (2000) argues that usability-based approaches are ‘limited, even dehumanizing’, as the user interacting is regarded only with ‘cognitive and physical characteristics’. He presents the *Four Pleasures Framework* to expand this perspective and include psychological aspects in order to understand users more realistically. Jordan distinguishes between four types of pleasure in his classification:

- **Physio-pleasure.** The body and sensory organs, like tactile and olfactory stimuli, trigger this experience. A designer aiming at creating physio-pleasure needs to design surfaces, shapes, smells, and further embodiment characteristics according to the physical and physiological needs of the user.
- **Socio-pleasure.** This experience is triggered by relationships with other persons or society as a whole: a product facilitates social interactions — people want to feel a sense of belonging and social interaction.
- **Psycho-pleasure.** Psycho-pleasure experiences pertain to people’s cognitive and emotional reactions — they want to achieve certain goals and be proud. This experience is triggered by the judgment of process effectiveness and the results of a product interaction based on the user’s expectation. To achieve this, designers need to develop usable, efficient, and effective products that make users feel competent.
- **Ideo-Pleasure.** This experience is based on moral or ethical values, and personal aspirations, and how these are met by product interaction. The product can illustrate certain values through its physical appearance (e.g. sustainable materials for eco-design), but also the intangible brand image of a product.

Goals and Needs by Hassenzahl (2010)

For Hassenzahl (2010) the fulfillment of goals is a central issue of his book *Experience Design*. He distinguishes between three levels of goals based on Activity Theory by Kaptelinin & Nardi (2006) (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Three level hierarchy of goals by Hassenzahl (2010)

- **Lowest level: motor-goals.** On this level the goal and actions are more concrete with regard to a specific product: *How* does a user fulfill a goal? Different products thereby cause different motor-goals for the same do-goal: ‘making a call’ with a mobile phone, demands other operations than with the Skype application.
- **Middle level: do-goals.** This level of goals is labeled as the what-question: *What* does a user want to achieve? It is a concrete desired outcome of an action, independent from a concrete product or technology. For example, the do-goal of ‘making a call’ can be achieved by using a telephone or Skype.
- **Top level: be-goals.** This is the level that targets experiences: *Why* does a user want to achieve a goal? It relates to rather abstract user needs common for all humans. This is the level to start from when designing for experiences: asking what are the be-goals for the user and design based on those needs.

In order to design experiences starting with be-goals, Hassenzahl relates to a set of ten basic user needs, originally defined by Sheldon et al. (2001): autonomy, competence, relatedness, self-actualizing, security, luxury, popularity, physical thriving, self-esteem, and pleasure. He proposes bringing these needs into the interaction context and to derive product concepts fulfilling them.

Models Describing UX as Process

In contrast with the first section, the following models are more complex and describe user experience as the interplay of different influences over time. The framework by Khalid and Helander (2006) describes the evaluation of affective design from the designer and user perspective. Karapanos et al. (2009) focus on the change of user experience over time. *The Customer Experience Interaction Model* by von Saucken et al. (2012) integrates different discipline perspectives and theories on UX.

Figure 5. Framework for evaluation of affective design by Khalid & Helander (2006)

Framework for Evaluation of Affective Design by Khalid and Helander (2006)

A useful framework is outlined by Khalid & Helander (2006), labeled 'Framework for Evaluation of Affective Design' (Figure 5). This framework is descriptive and intends to outline issues that must be addressed in order to illustrate affective design from the *Designer's Environment* (left) and the *Affective User Experience* (right).

Within the designer's space three constraints exist including artifact design elements, context of use, and the social dimension. Artifact design elements refer to Norman's visceral, behavioral, and reflective characteristics that products will elicit during interaction (Norman, 2004). The context of use refers to the physical environment and situations in which the designer expects the user to interact with the product. Finally, the issue of trends, fashion, and social and cultural norms needs to be considered. For the user, individual user needs as well as the cognitive and affective systems will influence the emotional evaluation. Khalid & Helander surmise that users employ cognitive and affective channels to evaluate designs. The user's individual characteristics, like culture, propensity for creativity, and other attributes impact both cognitive and emotional evaluative channels.

Temporality of Experience by Karapanos et al. (2009)

Karapanos et al. (2009) proposed the 'Temporality of Experience' model (figure 6). Following the work of Silverston & Haddon (1996), Karapanos et al. identified three phases of product adoption including orientation, incorporation, and identification, which are driven by motivating forces including increasing familiarity, functional dependency, and emotional attachment that transition users from one phase to the next.

There is an initial stage identified as *Anticipation*, which results from the expectations prior to any physical experience

Figure 6. Temporality of experience by Karapanos et al. (2009)

with a device. *Orientation* refers to the initial experiences with the device, like the initial learning curve or excitement with new features. *Incorporation* reflects the stage when the device becomes more meaningful in the users' lives. During this stage, usability and usefulness become significant factors that impact experience. Finally the *Identification* phase ushers in acceptance of the device into the cultural and social fabric of life, communicating self-identity and serving to differentiate or connect to others.

Customer Experience Interaction Model CEIM by von Saucken et al. (2012)

The first integrated model we discuss is the *Customer Experience Interaction Model* (CEIM), by von Saucken et al. (2012). It provides a holistic view on the interaction of users with products. CEIM incorporates different relevant models and views from the disciplines of engineering, human factors, industrial design, and psychology. It supports the communication between developers by creating a common terminology (Figure 7).

CEIM is based on the ‘Block Diagram of Human Machine System’ by Schmidtke (1993) representing a classic ergonomics perspective with the goal to improve the working task fulfillment by adapting the machine, its interface, and the environment impact to the user’s capacity. It focuses the human machine interaction with relevant ports in between (sensory organs, muscular system, and user interface). Since user

experience requires a stronger consideration of the human perception and processing, CEIM details the user element by adding *emotions* and *motives*.

CEIM enlarges the functional understanding of products by *Indication, Aesthetic, and Symbolic* aspects according to Steffen (2000). User experience is more than just fulfilling tasks in a most efficient manner. The emotional value and experience by using an expensive sports car can be the result not only of great driving properties (practical function), but also of the pleasant exterior and interior design considering shape and materials (aesthetic function), as well as the prestige through product and brand (symbolic function).

Macro UX and Micro UX

Similar to the ‘Framework of Product Experience’ by Desmet & Hekkert (2007), we perceive in essence two different but integrated levels by which users experience products that we call *Macro* and *Micro UX*. We can observe experiences that are mainly driven by the context of use — by other people, brand values, culture, external influences, and so on, and we categorize this level as *Macro UX*. At this level the product is the enabler or mediator of its purpose and function, and the experience would not arise without the context. Those experiences are processed on the reflective and behavioral level (Norman, 2004) and relate mainly to psycho- and ideopleasures (Jordan, 2000). They are long-term experiences and fulfill be-goals (Hassenzahl, 2010).

In contrast, *Micro UX* is directly caused by the product interaction, and the corresponding product’s embodiment within the immediate environment of the user. These experiences correspond to Norman’s (2004) visceral level and cause aesthetic experiences (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007), as well as relating to physio-pleasure (Jordan, 2000). These experiences are caused by the product’s embodiment, are generally experienced in a short amount of time and influence motor-goals

Figure 7. Customer Experience Interaction Model CEIM by von Saucken et al. (2012)

CRITERIA	MACRO UX	MICRO UX
UX approach	Creating a big picture of UX and deriving product concepts	Proposing UX improvement and avoiding UX violation in detail
User goals	Be-goals (why user wants it)	Motor-goals (how user uses it)
Relationship	User-Product-Context over time	User-Product interaction
Impacts	Evaluation of overall experience	Interaction
Starting point	Predefined set of user needs	Existing product design
Result	Effective UX	Efficient UX
Influence	Product concept and functions	Product embodiment design
Development phase	Early stage of goal setting	Embodiment design, optimization
Time span	Long-term: consideration during whole design process necessary	Short-term: occasional support during several stages possible
Abstraction level	Rather abstract (goals, purpose)	Concrete hints for design
Opportunity	Radical UX innovation	Only incremental UX innovation
Risk	High, changes entire product	Low, just improvement in detail

Table 1. Comparison of Macro UX and Micro UX by von Saucken et al. (2013a)

(Hassenzahl, 2010). The differences between Macro and Micro UX are outlined in Table 1. It is important to identify the differences between these two levels as they form the basis of the model presented in this paper. However, it is their integration and the way that both levels interact that is most relevant for understanding an authentic user experience.

UNIFYING TWO USER EXPERIENCE MODELS

We present a synthesis of two models of user experience developed by the authors (Figures 8 and 9) in an attempt to conceptualize the complexity of the user experience. Firstly, von Saucken et al. (2013b) developed the *UXIM* as a refined version of the *CEIM* (Figure 7) presented earlier, which focused on the user-product interaction. The models are descriptive and mention context (physical and social for instance), but context is not further detailed or structured. This is where the *DE³* framework by Gomez (2012) is used to support the model developed by von Saucken et al., but is itself more predictive and thereby supports design synthesis. Through the unification of the two models, the *Unified User Experience Model* (Figure 10) is presented.

User Experience Interaction Model UXIM by von Saucken (2013b)

CEIM (Figure 7) was evaluated in several industrial and student projects with the task of supporting user experience (UX) design. UX aspects were missing and several opportunities for improvement were defined:

- A descriptive model needs to cover the *temporal* aspect of UX beyond the actual interaction: people can have an experience before their first encounter through expectations formed from existing experience of related technologies, brand, advertisements, or others' opinions. Similarly, indirect experience extends after usage through reflection on previous usage, or through changes in people's appraisals of use (Karapanos et al., 2009; Roto et al., 2011).
- The inner representation of the used product, or *mental model*, has a strong impact on UX. Users derive a men-

tal model from their observation of the product (Norman, 2004). This inner model need not necessarily be appropriate to what leads to confusion and frustration — a bad experience.

- UX focuses on triggering positive user emotions. These *emotions* need to be considered stronger than in CEIM. A differentiation between rational and emotional perception before, during, and after the interaction would offer a new perspective on the human perception and judgment of products.
- CEIM illustrates many relevant aspects of UX, but it is difficult to determine where exactly *User Experience* arises. The model gathers many different perspectives, but is difficult to explain to people without previous knowledge. Furthermore, the illustration is text-based. A model should be more figurative and thereby intuitively understood.

We enriched CEIM with these insights to develop the 'User Experience Interaction Model' (UXIM) (Figure 8). It consists of three UX-relevant parts: the *interaction* of user and product (center, considering rational and emotional processing), the *temporal* perspective on the experience (left, expectation before usage and remembrance after usage), and the surrounding *environment* (right, including social influences and service systems). Additionally, we include the *mental model*, as it strongly influences the experience.

The illustrated user interacting with the product (represented by a laptop) takes the center stage. User and product are linked via a classic ergonomics cycle according to Schmidtke's (1993) ports: the user performs an action with the product using its input devices. The product carries out a function and returns the result via the output device. This is perceived and processed (interpreted) by the user leading to new actions. We included the enlarged function perspective of Steffen (2000) by adding the arrows *Aesthetics* and *Prestige*.

As UX is a subjective emotional reaction within the user, we get more into detail regarding the processing element: on the one hand, we distinguish between three time spans, represented by the cycle on the left side — before, during, and after usage (Roto et al., 2011). On the other, we divide the

Figure 8. User Experience Interaction Model UXIM by von Saucken et al. (2013b)

Figure 9. Designing for evolving emotional experiences (DE3) framework by Gomez (2012)

processing element into a rational-driven cycle (the external ring), and an emotional-driven (the internal ring). We included a representation of a *mental model* in the center of the processing cycle.

Designing for Evolving Emotional Experiences Framework (DE3) by Gomez (2012)

The framework ‘Designing for Evolving Emotional Experiences’ (DE3) was developed by Gomez (2012) from a study exploring two types of portable interactive devices (PIDs), and provides some principles when considering emotional experiences at the Micro and Macro levels of the UX (Figure 9).

On the top far left is the title *Personal or Social context* (user-product interface in context), which relates to the Macro UX, or Norman’s (2004) reflective level, and Hassenzahl’s (2010) be-goals. Essentially, the model identifies that social interactions (social contexts) impacted the overall emotional experience to a large degree, varying slightly for each product category. Personal interactions (private contexts) did not impact the overall emotional experience to the same degree. Below that, on the bottom far left is the box explaining the findings relevant for the *User-product interface*, relating to the Micro UX, Norman’s (2004) visceral and behavioural levels, and Hassenzahl’s (2010) motor and do-goals. Principles for promoting positive experiences and avoiding negative experiences are provided as recommendations.

To promote positive UX, the following aspects with *Mediation* and *Functional* categories must be considered:

- **Mediation:** From the outset consider how the device will mediate (facilitate) experiences beyond the functional.
- **Functional:** Make certain that the device performs its core function well.

To avoid negative UX the following aspects regarding *Features* and *Auxiliary* categories must be considered:

- **Features:** Reduce the number of additional features on the device.
- **Auxiliary:** Consider creating service for auxiliary (tertiary) activities of the device.

Overall the DE3 framework attempts to combine the Micro and Macro levels to form a holistic relationship and provide relevant recommendations. The DE3 model is designed to enable designers, and design researchers, to conceptualise and frame the design of devices to promote positive emotional experiences, and reduce negative emotional experiences, at the Micro and the Macro UX level.

The Unified User Experience Model

The UXIM and DE3 presented above (Figures 8 and 9), enriched with some of the principles and concepts of the models and frameworks presented earlier, were amalgamated into the *Unified User Experience Model* (Figure 10). The model aims to capture the complex, dynamic, evolving aspect of the experience over time. It is composed of both Micro and Macro UX level, which is argued to be a critical component for user experience.

The *Unified User Experience Model* frames von Saucken et al.’s (2013b) UXIM model at the center of the user experience and situates a variety of concepts from Gomez’s (2012) DE3 framework and the other models presented previously into the Micro and Macro UX. The model has been designed to be dynamic in nature by having the capacity to consider the model in different modes. Potentially, there are three modes that take into account the (a) user-product interaction, (b) user-product within the Micro UX context, and (c) user-product-Micro UX within the Macro UX context (Figure 11).

It is these various modes in combination that try and capture the complexity of the user and product interaction in context. Each mode can be understood separately but it is in considering the three collectively that provides a more holistic view of the user experience. The elements of the model can be explained based on the three layers described above.

- (a) **User-product interaction.** This is the same as the UXIM model presented earlier (Figure 8, von Saucken et al., 2013b). The three time spans: before, during, and after use, are present as the rational-driven cycle (external ring), and the emotional-driven cycle (internal ring). Representation of the user’s mental model is included within the processing cycle.

Figure 10. Unified User Experience Model (after Gomez, 2012; von Saucken et al., 2013b)

Figure 11. Three modes: (a) user-product interaction, (b) user-product within Micro UX and (c) user-product-Micro UX within Macro UX

(b) **User-product interaction within Micro UX.** Here the Micro level is introduced and pertains to the product interaction and the corresponding product's embodiment within the immediate environmental context of the user. These experiences correspond to Norman's (2004) visceral level and cause aesthetic experiences (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007) and relate to physio-pleasures (Jordan, 2000), caused by the product's design, influencing the motor-goals (Hassenzahl, 2010). The various elements include:

- **Co-existing Products.** Other products that impact the user-product interaction — for instance a computer mouse or external hard-drive when interacting with a personal computer.
- **Product Service.** The necessary services required for the product to function properly — for instance an electrical outlet to plug the personal computer into.

- **Persons / People.** Other persons who impact on the user-product interaction.
- **Physical Environment.** The immediate physical environment of the user-product interaction — for instance the physical room the personal computer is situated in.
- **Weather.** The immediate environmental climate impacting the user-product interaction — for instance, if the interaction is occurring outside, rain or other conditions may prohibit activity completely.
- **Light.** The available light, natural or artificial, that is available for the user-product interaction to occur.

It is proposed that the Micro UX level impacts the immediate interaction between user and product, and although it can lead to emotional experiences, these are short-lived and may not go on to impact the emotional experience in the long term.

(c) **User-product-Micro within Macro UX.** This mode takes into account the entire model and is conceptually where the product becomes an enabler or mediator of its purpose and function within a given context. Those experiences are processed on the reflective and behavioral level (Norman, 2004), and relate primarily to psycho, social, and ideo-pleasures (Jordan, 2000). They are rather long-term experiences and fulfill be-goals (Hassenzahl, 2010). The various elements identified include:

- **Supersystem.** Other products and services that are coordinated within an integrated service system
- **Brand.** The brand (and associated values) and its influence on the user's longer-term choices, decisions, and interactions with current and future products and services.
- **Social.** The social environment in which the user is interacting within — for instance, is the experience occurring at home, in the office, in public, etc.
- **Culture.** Any cultural context that impacts the user-product interaction — for instance different cultural values that may exist in other countries.
- **Values.** The user's personal moral and ethical values that impact their choices in a general way — for instance, is the user environmentally conscious?
- **Service.** Specific facilities offered by the product or company above and beyond the product's functions and features — for instance, an extended warranty service.
- **Time.** This deals with the fact that interactions occur over time and as such are constantly changing, morphing, and ultimately evolving during this period.

It is proposed that the Macro UX level influences interactions more generally and impacts the emotional experience in the long-term.

IMPLICATIONS FOR DESIGN

The *Unified User Experience Model* aims to better capture and represent the complex, dynamic, evolving aspect of the user experience over time. It is dynamic in nature and composed of both Micro and Macro UX levels, which are argued to be critical when conceptualizing the actual experience. It is hoped that the model will enable designers to better analyze existing designs and develop novel designs that comprehensively consider the full complexity of the user experience. The model takes into account some of the most relevant elements from the prominent models and frameworks available in the literature, and amalgamates two existing models; the UXIM model developed by von Saucken et al. (2013b), and the DE3 framework developed by Gomez (2012).

From the outset it is maintained that the model expands the current understanding of UX and sets the standard for capturing the full complexity of the actual user product interaction. Further, the model aims to enable designers from various fields to better examine existing products, interfaces,

and systems as well as assist designers to develop improved and novel designs that take into account a more comprehensive view of UX.

Future Study

The authors propose to conduct experiments analyzing the user-friendliness, usefulness, and effectiveness of the 'Unified User Experience Model', with designers concurrently in Australia and Germany, so as to mitigate any potential limitations. To begin with, the model will be analyzed with design students in both countries to see how well the model works with less experienced designers. Further, the model will be used by industry in Germany to investigate its effectiveness within the business world. Similarly, design professionals in Australia will examine its value within the industrial design discipline.

CONCLUSION

Design is about improving the life of people including making experiences with products, devices, and interfaces easy and usable as well as emotionally meaningful. User experience (UX) is understood in different ways by several disciplines. However, the motivation of UX is to enhance the overall experience and meet pragmatic, functional, as well as the psychological and emotional needs and motives of users (Hassenzahl, 2010). From a marketing perspective, by triggering the user's emotions and creating brand loyalty, UX can help differing products in saturated markets.

In this paper we propose an integrated and comprehensive model of experience covering the most prominent perspectives from across the design field. It can be argued that no model could ever encapsulate the true complexity and reality of individual human experience, yet the critical components that make up experiences such as context, dynamism, evolving, and time need to be incorporated into any framework that attempts to comprehensively consider the user product interaction. Nevertheless, we believe this model is a worthwhile attempt at capturing this complexity. It is intended to support designers from different disciplines in order to consider and deal with the complexity of UX. The vision is for the model, labeled 'Unified User Experience Model', to support both the analysis of existing products, interfaces, and systems as well as the development of new designs. In essence we hope the model can enable designers to develop more marketable, appropriate, and enhanced products to improve experiences, and ultimately the lives of people.

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TOUCH SENSATIONS IN AN ONLINE STORE. THE INFLUENCE OF IMAGE INTERACTIVITY ON EMOTIONAL EXPERIENCE AND PRODUCT EVALUATION

Suzanne Overmars, Karolien Poels
 University of Antwerp, Dept. Communication sciences
 City campus, Sint-Jacobstraat 2, 2000 Antwerp, Belgium
 ✉ Suzanne.Overmars@uantwerp.be, Karolien.Poels@uantwerp.be

ABSTRACT

In this study we build upon the persuasiveness of touch in product evaluations and extend it to an online store environment. We explore the contribution of image interactivity in mediated product experiences to perceived diagnosticity (i.e. the extent to which the shopping experience is deemed as helpful to evaluate the product), and emotional experience. Results of an experimental study (n=67) reveal that, compared to a static interface, an interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures led to higher levels of perceived diagnosticity and more favorable emotional responses. Additionally, little differences were observed between an interactive interface and actual touch. We also explore the moderating role of an individual's need for touch and conclude that an interactive interface is especially effective for consumers high in need of touch.

KEYWORDS: *touch; product experience; emotional responses; mediated environment; consumers*

INTRODUCTION

People tend to find personal experiences extremely compelling. Hoch (2002, p.448) even states that consumers are 'too trusting of what they have learned through experience'. This is one of the reasons why consumers' *direct* experience with a product, in which they continuously receive information through various senses, has proven to be highly persuasive (Smith, 1993). Obviously, sensory aspects of a product such as smell, touch, looks, sound and taste strongly influence product evaluations (Balaji et al., 2011; Krishna et al., n.d.). Together with vision, the tactile sense in particular is recognized as an important sensor to pass on acceptance (Sheldon & Arens, 1932). Our sense of touch 'provides us with information about the world, about the shape and weight of things, about its texture and temperature, its verticality and stability, and many other physical properties' (Hekkert, 2006, p.162). Touch can at times even directly compete with visual input. For example, Balaji and colleagues (2011) have shown that touch rather than vision is a preferred sensory modality for acquiring relevant information for products with important material properties, such as texture, hardness, and temperature. In a similar vein, recent research supports the idea that touch

is highly effective in influencing decision making, resulting in favorable consumer responses (Grohmann et al., 2007; McCabe & Nowlis, 2003). Touch can thus be used as a powerful product communication tool. Traditional brick-and-mortar stores are able to excite consumers through all their senses. However, online stores are limited in the sensory information they can offer. People can, for example, not physically handle products. This lack of direct experiential information is one of the main reasons why consumers remain hesitant to buy their products online (Citrin et al., 2003). As such, online retailers are challenged to integrate features in the online store to let consumers experience products 'as if they are real'. Hence, it is worthwhile looking for a substitute for touch since its underlying mechanisms could provide similar effects, in a mediated way, as actual touch. Remarkably, little is known about the role of (or the lack of) touch in product judgments and decision making in an online environment and how online retailers can overcome, or at least decrease, this barrier by providing mediated touch.

Building further upon the persuasiveness of touch, the primary objective of this study is to demonstrate that an interface with *image interactivity* to simulate stroking gestures can tap into tactile perceptual information and in this way affect product

understanding and emotional responses. Furthermore, it is expected that the effect of image interactivity on emotional responses is more apparent for people who have a chronic preference for hedonic aspects of touch, such as seeking fun, arousal, and excitement.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Interdependence between touch and vision

Information gathered through vision and touch partly overlaps. Therefore, vision is considered to offer an alternative exploratory option that could be used in conjunction with, or instead of, tactile exploration (Yazdanparast & Spears, 2012). For example, the steam rising from a cup of tea tells us something about the temperature of that cup. Further, Klatzky et al. (1991) suggest that, when deprived of ‘actual’ touch, mental tactile exploration during visual imagery provides access to information about tactually accessible object attributes (e.g., roughness of a tennis ball). In the same way, Anema and colleagues (2012) demonstrated that visual stimuli are able to guide thinking about touch elements, which subsequently facilitates tactile sensations. More specifically, participants reported they could vividly feel the sensation to the skin when visualizing grasping a hand full of the gravel depicted in a picture, despite the fact that there was no actual tactile stimulus present. In fact, studies in the field of neuroscience have revealed considerable overlap between tactile imagery and neural mechanisms underlying real tactile perception, insofar as it activates at least some of the same brain areas (Keyes et al., 2004; Spence & Gallace, 2011). Hence, sensory input in one modality is capable of eliciting an experience in a different sensory modality. However, research on visual input and feelings of touch is mostly limited to static images. The role of image interactivity in inducing mediated touch sensations remains relatively unexplored, despite recent important technological advances.

Image interactivity & perceived diagnosticity

If actual touch affects product judgments and decision making, could an interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures have a similar effect? The present study adopts *image interactivity* in a mediated environment as a way to induce some of the stimulation consumers normally derive from product touch. Steuer (1992, p.84) defines interactivity as ‘the extent to which users can participate in modifying the form or content of a mediated environment in real time’. Image interactivity allows the user to directly manipulate objects in a virtual environment. As a result, there is a continuous change in graphics that bear a close resemblance to physical actions — as if events are occurring in the physical world (Schlosser, 2003). Most online stores currently employ a basic form of image interactivity technology (e.g., a static image with an extensive zoom). However, advanced image interactivity allows users to manipulate and modify the form of an object more

directly; an example of an advanced image interactivity interface is the Shoogleit¹, see Figure 1. The interactive interface allows users to ‘move’ fabric by dragging their mouse, hence simulating stroking gestures. Such a new digitally interactive way to represent objects has been proposed to be able to bring the digital experience of products closer to reality (Wu et al., 2011). In this paper we set out to investigate whether it can provide consumers with similar kinds of information normally available through direct experiential contact with the product (e.g., fabric flexibility or softness).

Fig. 1. Example of the image interactivity interface

Continuing with the above reasoning, a product experience is deemed as helpful and relevant when the experience serves an informational function for consumers considering a purchase (Kempf & Smith, 1998; Lee et al., 2012). That’s exactly what perceived diagnosticity is about. Perceived diagnosticity is conceptualized as ‘the perceived ability of the shopping experience to provide relevant product information to help consumers accurately evaluate product attributes’ (Lee et al., 2012, p.382). Some product attributes (e.g., texture, softness, flexibility) can be evaluated only by using the product directly, also known as *experience attributes* (Nelson, 1974). Critical to the value of this experience is the perceived diagnosticity of information gathered through touch in helping to make informed product decisions. Interfaces generating high levels of image interactivity allow users to manipulate a product in an online environment. The interactive cues may generate a

1 Surf for an interactive example to http://www.shoogleit.com/2622-o_NOORA-sjaal

vivid, informative, and impressive presentation of the product. We hypothesize that an interactive interface will be perceived as diagnostic when evaluating experience attributes because image interactivity conveys tactile information on these attributes, while a static interface does not. Furthermore, an interactive interface may sufficiently capture experience attributes in such a way that touching the actual product doesn't provide more information.

H1: An interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures significantly increases perceived diagnosticity of experience attributes, compared to a regular interface with only static images.

Emotional responses

Thus far, we have focused on the informational function of touch. However, studies have also found an immediate, automatic emotional response toward the touched object (Peck & Shu, 2009; Peck & Wiggins, 2006). Emotions can be elicited through a stimulation of our senses by product appearance (Isbister et al., 2007). Tactile input in particular is linked to affect and plays an important role in how consumers perceive products (Jansson-Boyd, 2011). More specifically, by altering the tactile surfaces, it has been proposed that it is possible to make consumers feel connected to a product on an emotional level (Jansson-Boyd, 2011; Sonneveld & Schifferstein, 2008). For example, an empirical study (Essick et al., 1999) has shown that soft and smooth fabric materials were consistently perceived as more pleasant to touch than those that were stiff, rough or coarse. Touching a pleasantly valenced object can result in positive emotional responses toward the object even if touch elements provide no information regarding the product (Peck & Shu, 2009). These hedonic aspects of touch thus seem to appear independent of the informational function of touch. Therefore, an interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures is expected to compensate for a lack of touch, and in this way may serve as a substitute for touch in order to enjoy the hedonic aspect of product experiences.

H2: An interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures results in more positive emotional responses during product evaluation compared to a regular interface with only static images.

Additionally, emotions play a role when consumers are prevented from touching products, as is the case in online environments, affecting the judgment decisions that they make (Jansson-Boyd, 2011). If consumers feel the need to touch products and are not allowed to do so, it can lead to a strong sense of dissatisfaction, a negative emotional response, making them avoid mediated shopping environments (Citrin et al., 2003; McCabe & Nowlis, 2003). Hence, we hypothesize that different from a static interface, an interactive interface simulating stroking gestures is able to reduce negative feelings, because the interactive cues emphasize tactile information.

H3: An interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures results in less negative emotions during product evaluation compared to a regular interface with

only static images.

Need for touch

Individuals differ in their predilection for tactile information; hence the effects of touch differ across people. Peck and Childers (2003a, p. 431) identify individual differences in need for touch (NFT), that is, 'a person's preference for the extraction and utilization of information obtained through touch'. Furthermore, NFT is conceptualized as having two dimensions: instrumental NFT and autotelic NFT (Peck & Childers, 2003a). In this study we focus on the autotelic dimension of NFT. Individuals who are high in autotelic NFT engage in touch because it is fun, an experience that is far more hedonic than instrumental. An individual who is high in autotelic NFT often feels an irresistible need to engage in exploratory touch and is focused on the sensory aspects of touch as an end in itself (Peck & Wiggins, 2006). An interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures is expected to compensate for a lack of touch primarily for high autotelic haptically motivated consumers. Such an interactive interface would be expected to satisfy people who have a chronic preference for hedonic aspects of touch such as seeking fun, arousal, and excitement. In the same way, when this specific group of consumers is deprived of tactile stimulation (only static images are present) they can feel strong negative emotions precisely because an enjoyable substitute for touch is lacking. However, individuals who are low in autotelic NFT do not find touch as inherently interesting or as irresistible. Consequently, compensation for a lack of touch is not as important for consumers who are low in autotelic NFT.

H4: Compared to a regular interface with only static images, an interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures will (a) increase positive emotions (b) decrease negative emotions for people who are high in autotelic NFT, but will not affect emotional responses for those who are low in autotelic NFT.

METHOD

Participants and design

Only female participants were selected to eliminate gender-specific preference for the product since it was a feminine item. Accordingly, 67 female undergraduates participated in a twenty-minute experiment conducted in a controlled laboratory environment. All participants received a participation fee of five euros. A quasi-experiment, consisting of a 3 (mediated touch: static interface, mediated touch: interactive interface, actual touch) X 2 (low vs. high NFT) between-subjects design was employed wherein NFT reflects a person's chronic preference to touch. Inclusion of an 'actual touch condition' as a control condition enables us to compare the effects of image interactivity with the effects of actually handling the product.

Stimuli

Experimental product. A scarf was used as the experimental product. Research has consistently shown that clothing is clearly a product category for which tactile input is diagnostic in the evaluation processes (Grohmann et al., 2007; Jansson-Boyd, 2011). A pretest among 56 female students ($M_{\text{age}}=22.29$) was conducted to verify if scarfs would be an appropriate product category. The first objective was to test if tactile input is diagnostic for scarfs. A 7-point Likert scale measured mode of product evaluation (e.g. 'It is difficult to judge the quality of a scarf through visual inspection alone', based on a scale applied in Smith & Park, 1992). The average score was significantly higher than the neutral point (i.e., $H_0: M_x = 4$; $M_{\text{mode}}=4.84$, $t_{(55)}=4.87$, $p<.001$), which implies that participants indicated that various attributes of a scarf must be assessed through actual trial and not through visual inspection alone. The second objective of the pretest was to determine the salient attributes to evaluate a scarf. Through a free elicitation assignment, participants were asked to list product attributes that they thought were important to consider for the selection of a scarf. The pretest results showed that material, warmth, softness, and thickness of the scarf could be identified as experience attributes most important to product choice.

Product presentation manipulation. We manipulated the product presentation by creating two mediated product experiences as experimental conditions. Two webpages of a fictitious online store were designed. In the 'mediated touch: static interface' condition (www.static.uasurvey.be), the product was displayed on a webpage accompanying the scarfs' picture and a picture of some details of the scarf. The webpage also included an extensive zoom option similar to webpages of currently available online stores. In the 'mediated touch: interactive interface' condition (www.uasurvey.be), the scarf was displayed on a webpage in the same way as in the static interface condition, the only difference being that users were allowed to modify the form of the product by using the Shoogle. As control condition we created an actual product experience, wherein participants were able to physically examine the actual scarf. To provide all participants with identical written product information, a product label containing a written description similar to the description on the webpage was attached to the scarf.

Procedure

Participants were invited to visit a lab individually and sat at a table in front of a computer monitor. Potential intervening variables such as browser type (chrome 31.0.1650.63 m), Internet connection speed, and instructions were kept constant. Participants were randomly assigned to one of the three conditions. To be sure all participants were sufficiently involved in the evaluation task, participants could choose to take part in a price drawing (instructions can be found in appendix A). In this way, a relevant product evaluation situation was created (i.e., participants had to consider if they found the scarf worthy/valuable enough to participate in the price drawing). Subsequently, participants either saw the product presented on a

webpage or had the opportunity to actually touch the product (the participants were instructed to take the scarf out of the drawer, so touch was assured). After a 1 ½ minute product examination, participants filled out measures relating to the dependent variables of the study. After completing the questionnaire, participants were debriefed and thanked.

Measures

All of the following measures were adapted from pre-validated measures in consumer behavior studies. Below is a brief description, more details for all measures can be found in Appendix B.

Manipulation checks. To verify whether the manipulation of involvement was successful, participants were asked to fill in a scale based on Pham, 1996 ($\alpha=.80$). Subsequently, to assess the level of perceived feelings of touch for participants in the mediated conditions, a measure developed by Peck and colleagues (2013) was used ($\alpha=.82$).

Perceived diagnosticity. In this study, perceived diagnosticity was measured at the attribute rather than product level. We measured perceived diagnosticity across the scarf's salient experience attributes: material, warmth, thickness, and softness. The four items were averaged for a measure of perceived diagnosticity ($\alpha=.81$).

Emotional responses. Emotional responses were measured using the visual self-report instrument PrEmo (Desmet, 2003), containing six positive and six negative emotions. We averaged the positive emotions for a measure of positive responses ($\alpha=.82$), and did the same for a measure of negative responses ($\alpha=.75$).

Need for touch. Participants had to complete the autotelic component of the NFT scale ($\alpha=.89$) developed by Peck and Childers (2003a).

RESULTS

Manipulation checks

Involvement. A one sample t-test revealed that the average score on involvement was significantly higher than the neutral point (i.e., $H_0: M_x=4$; $M_{\text{inv}}=5.32$, $t_{(66)}=11.69$, $p<.01$), suggesting that participants were sufficiently involved in evaluating the product thoroughly. Results of an ANOVA revealed no significant differences between the three conditions with regard to the level of involvement ($F_{(2,64)}=0.77$, NS).

Perceived feeling of touch. A t-test was run and a significant effect of product presentation on perceived feelings of touch was found ($t_{(42)}=-4.64$, $p<.001$, $\eta^2=.34$). As expected, an interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures resulted in significantly greater perceived feelings of touch than a static interface (see figure 2), implying that participants in the interactive condition reported more frequently that they actually had the feeling of the scarf in their hands.

Fig. 2. Mean perceived feelings of touch by product presentation.

Perceived diagnosticity

H1 predicted that participants would find an interactive interface more diagnostic for experience attributes during product evaluation than a static interface. As expected, the effect of product presentation on perceived diagnosticity of experience attributes was highly significant ($F_{(2,64)}=13.72, p<.001$, partial $\eta^2=.30$). Planned contrasts revealed that the mean score of participants after exposure to an interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures was higher ($M=4.90$) than the mean score of participants after exposure to a regular interface with only static images ($M=3.89; t_{(64)}=3.45, p<.01, r=.40$). Subsequently, we observed no significant difference in perceived diagnosticity between the interactive interface condition and the condition where actual touch was possible ($M=5.38; t_{(64)}=1.66, NS$). The results indicate that participants who interact with an interface simulating stroking gestures perceived the product experience as highly diagnostic for product attributes such as thickness and softness, which was similar to participants who actually handled the product.

Fig. 3. Mean emotional responses for static and interactive condition

Positive emotional responses

H2 stated that simulating stroking gestures using image interactivity would result in more positive emotional responses. To test this proposition, an ANOVA was performed with an averaged measure of positive emotional response as the dependent variable, and product presentation as the independent variable. The results revealed a significant main effect for positive emotional responses ($F_{(2,63)}=4.14, p<.05, \eta^2=.12$). Overall, participants reported positive emotional responses when they could physically touch the product ($M=1.71$). When participants used an interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures during product evaluation they reported even slightly more positive emotional responses ($M=1.95$). However, when tactile information was limited because the product was presented by means of a regular interface with only static images, positive emotional reactions dropped considerably ($M=1.29$). As expected, planned contrast tests revealed that an interactive interface elicited more positive emotional responses than a static interface ($t_{(63)}=2.84, p<.01, r=.34$). Positive emotional responses elicited by the interactive interface, again, did not differ from that of actual product interactions ($t_{(63)}=1.01, NS$). Subsequently, in order to establish whether responses differed over product presentation for each specific emotion, a MANOVA was performed with six positive emotional responses as dependent variables, and product presentation as an independent variable. Using Pillai's trace, there was a significant main effect for positive emotional responses ($V=0.62, F_{(12,118)}=4.45, p<.001$, partial $\eta^2=.31$). Looking at the emotions individually using separate univariate ANOVAs, we learned that desire ($F_{(2,63)}=5.12, p<.01$, partial $\eta^2=.14$), fascination ($F_{(2,63)}=5.01, p<.01$, partial $\eta^2=.14$), and joy ($F_{(2,63)}=11.02, p<.001$, partial $\eta^2=.26$) are important emotional responses to touch experiences. The emotions, satisfaction, pride, and hope are less relevant because the effect of product presentation on these three specific emotions failed to reach significance ($p>.12$). Planned contrast tests revealed that an interactive interface significantly ($M=1.64$) increased feelings of desire compared to a static

Fig. 4. Mean emotional responses for actual and interactive condition

interface ($M=.73$; $t_{(63)}=2.77$, $p<.01$, $r=.33$). Furthermore, an interactive interface can elicit feelings of desire in the same way as actual touch ($M=1.64$; $t_{63}=0.00$, *NS*), whereas a static interface almost entirely fails to elicit feelings of desire. The same pattern is true for joy (see Figure 3 and Figure 4). Likewise, an interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures elicits fascination to a greater extent than a static interface does ($t_{(63)}=2.97$, $p<.01$, $r=.37$). Interestingly, participants in the interactive condition are significantly more fascinated than participants in the actual condition ($t_{(63)}=2.43$, $p<.05$, $r=.29$).

Negative emotional responses

H3 predicted that an interactive interface is capable of suppressing negative emotional responses typically elicited by the absence of tactile information. To test this assumption an ANOVA was performed with an averaged measure of negative emotional responses as the dependent variable and product presentation as the independent variable. A significant main effect was found ($F_{(2,63)}=6.94$, $p<.01$, $\eta^2=.18$). As predicted, a regular interface with only static images elicited the most negative emotional responses ($M=0.71$). While both actual touch ($M=0.15$), and an interactive interface simulating stroking gestures ($M=0.34$), elicited less negative emotional responses. Planned contrast tests show that a static interface elicited significantly more negative emotional responses than the interactive interface ($t_{(32)}=2.07$, $p<.05$, $r=.25$), whereas participants who physically examined the product reported levels of negative emotional responses similar to participants who used the interactive interface ($t_{(35)}=1.88$, *NS*). These results support H3. To further inspect specific negative emotions a MANOVA was performed with six negative emotional responses as dependent variables and product presentation as independent variable. Overall, using Pillai's trace a significant main effect of product presentation on negative emotional responses was found ($V=0.38$, $F_{(12,118)}=2.33$, $p<.01$, partial $\eta^2=.19$). Separate univariate ANOVAs reveal that disgust ($F_{(2,63)}=4.85$, $p<.05$, partial $\eta^2=.13$), dissatisfaction ($F_{(2,63)}=9.03$, $p<.001$, partial $\eta^2=.22$), shame ($F_{(2,63)}=3.18$, $p<.05$, partial $\eta^2=.09$), fear ($F_{(2,63)}=3.35$, $p<.05$, partial $\eta^2=.10$), and boredom ($F_{(2,63)}=4.91$, $p<.01$, partial $\eta^2=.14$) are important emotional drivers of negative responses elicited by product presentation. Planned contrast tests reveal that a static interface provoked far more feelings of dissatisfaction ($M=0.91$) than an interactive interface simulating stroking gestures ($M=0.23$; $t_{(32)}=2.79$, $p<.01$, $r=.44$). While the latter provoked similar low levels of dissatisfaction as actually handling the product ($M=0.09$; $t_{(33)}=1.06$, *NS*). In the same way, participants exposed to a static interface were clearly more bored ($M=1.59$) than participants exposed to an interactive interface ($M=0.59$; $t_{(63)}=2.89$, $p<.01$, $r=.34$). Whereas the difference in boredom between an interactive interface and actually handling the product ($M=0.97$) proved to be non-significant ($t_{(63)}=0.39$, *NS*). See Figures 3 and 4 for a graphic display of the results.

Moderating role of NFT

In this paragraph we focus on the moderating role of autotelic NFT in mediated product experiences. To distinguish

between participants high in autotelic NFT, compared to those low in autotelic NFT, the variable was dichotomized based on a median split ($Mdn=5.83$; $M_{highNFT}=6.37$, $M_{lowNFT}=4.93$; $t_{(65)}=-11.28$, $p<.001$). The moderating role of NFT on actual product experiences is already established in literature (Peck & Childers, 2003a, 2003b). Therefore, and for reasons of brevity, we decided not to include the actual touch condition in the following analyses.

H4a predicted that compared to a regular interface with only static images, an interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures would increase positive emotions for people who are in autotelic NFT, but will not result in more positive emotions for those who are low in autotelic NFT. However, the interaction effect between product presentation and autotelic NFT showed to be non-significant ($F_{(2,62)}=1.37$, *NS*), providing no support for autotelic NFT affecting positive emotional responses (H4a is rejected).

On the contrary, when examining the effect of autotelic NFT and product presentation on negative emotions, we detected a significant interaction effect ($F_{(1,40)}=6.38$, $p<.05$, partial $\eta^2=.14$). Follow-up tests for the interaction effect conducted separately for the two autotelic NFT groups showed that for individuals low in NFT, negative emotional responses were not dependent on whether they were able to interact with an interface simulating stroking gestures, as the means did not differ significantly, see Figure 5 ($t_{(20)}=-0.16$, *NS*). However, as expected, participants high in autotelic NFT experienced far less negative emotions when using an interactive interface simulating stroking gestures ($M=0.18$), rather than using a static interface ($M=1.02$, $t_{(9)}=2.69$, $p<.05$, $r=.50$). These results confirm H4b.

Fig. 5. Interaction effect product presentation x autotelic NFT

DISCUSSION

Whether we touch to obtain information or to enjoy sensory feedback, touch plays a vital role in our decision-making process (Jansson-Boyd, 2011; Peck et al., 2013). Acknowledging

that actual touch is not always feasible, we built on research that has focused on tactile perceptual information provided through the sense of vision and extended it to the online shopping environment. With the help of Shoogleit we designed an interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures to provide consumers with tactile information in a mediated environment. Results reveal that such an interactive interface can in fact compensate for an inability to touch in a number of respects.

First, an interactive interface has shown to offer an informational function for experience attributes. An interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures provides relevant product attribute information and is therefore perceived as highly diagnostic during product evaluation. In other words, the interactive cues seem to generate a vivid, informative, and impressive presentation of the product, and accordingly help consumers to intuitively gather information about texture, softness, and temperature. In line with our expectations, we found that image interactivity simulating stroking gestures can have similar effects on perceived diagnosticity, such as actual touch. These findings point to the significance of (interactive) visual stimuli capable of guiding thinking about touch elements as a significant process in mediated product experiences.

Second, emotional responses are regarded as one of the factors that contribute to the general superiority of direct experience over mediated experiences (Millar & Millar, 1996). Accordingly, an important question is whether an interactive interface can elicit emotional responses in the same way as actual touch. As to positive emotions we found that an interface simulating stroking gestures using image interactivity can elicit more positive emotional responses than a static interface. Image interactivity seems to sufficiently elicit positive emotional responses in such a way that touching the actual product does not arouse more positive emotions. Furthermore, we found no support for autotelic NFT affecting positive emotional responses. That is to say, image interactivity has a positive effect on emotional responses regardless of consumers' autotelic NFT. These results indicate that, against expectations, also for less haptically motivated consumers, an interactive interface elicits more positive emotional responses than a static interface. This may indicate that a static interface does not satisfy the basic needs for autotelic haptic information, even for individuals low in NFT. On the other hand, this effect may also be partly due to the 'newness' of the technology. Image interactivity itself is not a novel technology but the way it is applied in our study might have surprised the participants, which may have translated into positive emotional responses.

For negative emotional responses we found that consumers experience undesirable and unfavorable emotional responses when the ability to handle a product or interact with an interface simulating stroking gestures was denied. This pattern is particularly true for consumers high in autotelic NFT. The significant interaction effect tells us that consumers high in autotelic NFT experience more negative emotions when they use a static interface than when they use an interactive inter-

face. An interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures has thus proven to reduce negative feelings for consumers high in autotelic NFT because the interactive cues apparently emphasize hedonic tactile information. Consumers low in NFT, however, are less negatively affected by the lack of opportunity to use an interactive interface. The level of image interactivity did not significantly affect negative emotional responses for those who are low in autotelic NFT. From this we can conclude that the 'newness' of the technology most likely did not affect the results. The interactive interface is capable of inducing mediated touch sensations to some extent because in the context of this study it affected consumers high in NFT in particular. However, for consumers high in autotelic NFT the results underscore that an interactive interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures does mainly prevent them from experiencing negative emotions but does not particular excel in eliciting positive emotions any more than for consumers low in NFT.

Until now, it has been assumed that certain senses, such as touch, are extremely difficult to stimulate in mediated environments. Despite recent important technological advances, mediated touch sensations in an online store remain relatively unexplored. This study addresses the calls of Grohmann et al. (2007) and Jansson-Boyd (2011) to deepen our understanding of how to overcome the inherent inability to integrate tactile input into online shopping. The present study offers convincing arguments for the viability of image interactivity to tap into tactile perceptual information, hence, affecting consumer responses. In this way, the results provide promising evidence to support the growing field of sensory-based marketing communication and extend it to an online environment.

Limitations and future research

The present research is subject to several limitations that future researchers should consider. A main limitation lies in the fact that this study was restricted to a single product category (a scarf). As a result, the present findings may not be generalizable to other products. Future research, incorporating product type as a moderator, can shed light on boundary conditions in which mediated touch experiences are elicited and play a role in product evaluations. Furthermore, only female students participated in this study. Besides excluding gender-specific preference for the product, this choice was also based on the fact that women have proven to base their judgments more often on what they perceive sensorially than men (Schifferstein, 2006). Women attach a high importance to sensory modalities in product evaluations, while men are potentially less aware of their sensory processes, or find cognitive information (product packaging, advertising, recommendations of friends and family) more important. Therefore, women are particularly interesting in the context of this study because they have been thought to suffer the most when tactile information is lacking (Citrin et al., 2003). Future research should include men in the sample as well to examine if the results replicate well. As described earlier, in the context of this study we cannot fully exclude the effect of the 'newness' of the

technology. Familiarity with the interface may be considered as a control factor in further studies. Furthermore, we created an interface with image interactivity to simulate stroking gestures. Nonetheless, there are more common ways in which people handle fabric material (pinching, scrunching, rubbing, etc.). Future research could include an interactive interface simulating multiple gestures to test if it encourages users to behave in a manner even more similar to those observed in brick-and-mortar stores. We also acknowledge that only one sensory modality was explored, other sensory modalities could be of importance as well. Sound in particular has proven to be strongly related to tactile experience and can potentially excel effects of an interactive interface when combined.

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A PERSPECTIVE SHIFT FOR A HUMAN-LIFE-FRIENDLY PRODUCT SERVICE SYSTEM (PSS)

Jeong-Hyeon Kim, Kee-Ok Kim
Sungkyunkwan University
✉ jhkim1222@skku.edu, kokim@skku.edu

ABSTRACT

Sustainability has become an important issue for both producers and consumers. On the production side, the Product Service System (PSS) has targeted environmental protection, economic value, and consumer satisfaction, while consumers have also sought to minimize environmental repercussions while maintaining efficiency. The ultimate goal of the PSS is to promote both sustainable production and sustainable consumption, in that sustainable production can only be achieved when the life cycle includes sustainable consumption. In other words, the PSS should maintain environmental value while improving consumers' lives, and should influence not only the moment of consumption but also consumers' lives as a whole.

Based on this insight, PSS developers seek to understand and reflect the context of usage and consumers' needs from the beginning. However, these attempts are often considered only in terms of product or service usage, rather than in terms of human daily life or a comprehensive consumer life pattern. Human daily life consists of various activities, and these activities are related to one another. Therefore, the development of a human-life-friendly PSS can be easier considering the suggested point of view in this paper.

Therefore, this study selects and structures activities closely related to product service usage, and analyzes 59 PSS cases based on 61 consumer life domains selected from the American Time Use Survey (ATUS) Activity Coding Lexicon to identify which life domains a PSS can satisfy. By examining the differences in PSS offerings for specific activities, this research provides the basic information for successful human-life-friendly PSS development in the future.

KEYWORDS: *Product Service System, Human-life-friendly PSS, Sustainable consumption, Consumer life structure, Time use survey,*

INTRODUCTION

Sustainability has become an important issue for both production and consumption sides. On the production side, the Product Service System (PSS) has targeted environmental protection, economic value, and consumer satisfaction, while the consumption side has also sought to minimize environmental repercussions while maintaining efficiency. The PSS ultimate goal is to promote both sustainable production and consumption, in that sustainable production can only be achieved by sustainable consumption in terms of the life cycle. In other words, the PSS should be able to maintain environmental value while improving consumers' lives, and should influence not only the moment of consumption, but also the consumer's daily life as a whole.

Based on this insight, PSS developers seek to understand and reflect on the context of usage and the needs of consumers

from the beginning. However, these attempts are being considered only in terms of product or service usage, and not in terms of the daily life of a comprehensive consumer's life pattern. Human daily life consists of various activities, and these activities are related to one another. Therefore, the development of a human-life-friendly PSS should be easier if PSS developers consider how a consumer's life is composed, what kind of activities s/he is involved in, and how they are related to each other, as well as what elements of an individual's life can be improved upon.

Therefore, this study selects and structures the activities closely related to the usage of product service, and analyzes existing PSS cases based on the consumer life domain in order to identify the life domains that a PSS can or cannot satisfy. Also, by discovering the links between specific activities, this research suggests a possible consumer life domain for future successful human life-friendly PSS development. The research

will be conducted as follows: First, how a consumer's daily life is composed and how the components are linked will be examined. Time use surveys may be a useful tool for this. A time use survey is a survey that collects a country's detailed individual 24-hour activity records via record/interview methods for various purposes, and it is conducted at a nation-wide level in places like the US, Japan, Korea, and European countries. Methods and survey population size may vary in different countries. Data is collected by recording participants' activity over a 24-hour period into a diary with his/her demographic characteristics. The participants are required to record how, where, and with whom they spend their day in the diary.

Recorded content also includes non-market activities such as childcare and volunteer work. The Activity Lexicon, which will be used in this study, may be a useful reference to understand all of the activity elements that make up a subject's life. In order to structuralize consumers' daily lives, this research will use the 2012 American Time Use Survey (ATUS) Activity Coding Lexicon, which best categorizes activity elements in detail. The ATUS Activity Coding Lexicon is a three-tiered classification system with seventeen first-tier categories. Each of the first-tier categories has two additional levels of detail. Among these, activity elements that can be achieved using a product or service will be selected. Then, this research investigates which activity elements in a life structure are satisfied by 59 different business cases that employ the PSS concept. Each PSS case will then be categorized as product-oriented, use-oriented, or result-oriented, based on the providing-method classification suggested in Mont (2002) and Tukker (2004), and placed into a satisfying activity element.

If a case satisfies multiple activity elements, the case will be selected for all satisfied activity elements. After being analyzed, the results will be used to identify which activity is satisfied (or not satisfied) by PSS, and its main providing-method in terms of consumer life. Also, this paper will identify linkages between activities (whether one activity is linked with another simultaneously or chronologically) through time use survey panel data analysis, thus suggesting additional activities or challenging PSS providing-method on top of existing PSS activities. Moreover, using the linkage between activities, this paper will provide basic data for the development of new PSS ideas.

BACKGROUND

Sustainable consumption

While sustainable consumption has been officially emphasized since the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (the Rio Conference) in 1992, the individual ethics aspect of this subject has been studied from as early as the 1970s. Existing studies deal with the actions and motivations of consumers who consider the environment during the purchase, consumption, and disposal of a product (Anderson &

Cunningham, 1972; Henion, 1972; Webster, 1975). However, these studies focus on the motivation of a particular eco-friendly consumer group, thus emphasizing socioeconomic responsibility based on individual consumer's awareness.

More lively debate on sustainability in the consumer domain began to emerge in 1997 after the 1992 Rio Conference. Early studies were limited to improvements in the manufacturing process and reducing industrial waste; the focus has since shifted to the life cycle perspective, including both manufacturing and consumption, thus expanding the scope from the supply domain to include the consumer domain.

Sustainable development is thus recognized as requiring a dematerialized consumption pattern that can decrease resource and energy usage while considering the environmental repercussions of a product and its manufacturing process, and satisfying consumer needs. In light of this trend, the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) established its sustainable consumption program in 1998; many consumption-aspect studies have been conducted since (UNEP, 2002).

The early studies on sustainable consumption were mainly informational; governmental organizations conducted policy research and various NGOs created ethical guidelines to minimize consumption levels. Hansen and Schrader (1997), and Heiskanen and Pantzar (1997), developed a consumer behavior model of sustainable consumption. Moreover, studies have been conducted to determine the environmental affects of various consumption scenarios (Jager, 2000), to analyze resource- and energy-intensive consumption patterns, and to provide suggestions to address extreme consumption (Brown & Cameron, 2000; Røpke, 1999, 2001). However, while these attempts may have changed the public's perception of the subject matter, they failed to actualize a change in actual behavior patterns (Moisander, 2001). Most of these studies were limited to policy-level research (Mont, 2004).

During the mid-2000s, several scholars began to discuss ideas related to sharing-based collaborative consumption, founded on the spread of the Internet; hence, researchers started to focus on inducing changes in societal behavior. Collaborative consumption was initially defined as individual consumption of wealth or a service shared between individuals or multiple persons (Felson & Spaeth, 1978). This pattern of consumption activity must be dealt with in terms of both activities involving two individuals, and activities involving an individual and a society (Hawley, 1950); therefore, in order to understand collaborative consumption, both the consuming body and the specific context of the consumption activity, including location and precedents, must be considered (Felson & Spaeth, 1978).

These concepts of collaborative consumption, however, are limited to consumption behavior, and do not include the effectiveness of and satisfaction with such consumption behavior. Collaborative consumption has been out of discussion since the 2000s, when the rapid spread of the Internet led the term to be integrated with the notion of sharing. Belk (2007) defines sharing as an event in which more than two owners of the

same material benefit from cost-effectiveness, thus enhancing the consumption value. He suggested the idea of sharing as an alternative to private ownership, adding that effectiveness and satisfaction can be improved by sharing not only materials but also knowledge, liability, authority, voluntary leases, and resource allocation.

Lessig (2008) first introduced the term ‘sharing economy’, and proposed an economic system based on societal relations between communities — rather than on money — and increases the value of intangible/tangible wealth through sharing, exchange, lease, and utilization. However, Lessig’s (2008) work is limited to a theoretical suggestion.

The existing studies on sustainable consumption have involved conceptual discussion at the behavioral policy level, focusing on individual consumers or a specific moment of consumption; moreover, the preceding research is limited to alternatives in the consumption domain, and lacks a comprehensive life cycle perspective including manufacturing aspects. In order to promote realistic sustainable consumption, an eco-friendly product or service must not be limited to a specific moment of usage, but be expanded to be involved in overall daily life. Therefore, fundamental research reflecting consumers’ daily lives, and what type of life needs need to be satisfied, must be conducted. This information will allow developers to better understand consumers’ lives in terms of the consumption domain and can be incorporated at the development stage of a product/service.

Product Service System

The Product Service System (PSS), first introduced by Goedkoop (1999), is defined as a system that satisfies a customer’s needs and includes a product/service, and the relevant network and infrastructure developed to minimize environmental repercussions relative to the existing business model. Goedkoop proposed the PSS as an alternative to promote value by linking products and services, thus actualizing economic value and minimizing environmental damage simultaneously.

Mont (2002) collected various studies related to the PSS concept and put them together under the PSS system. Mont pointed out that existing studies involved only a single element — such as product usage, leasing, maintenance, and service — and that when all elements were integrated into one system with the product-service life cycle perspective, both environmental concerns and the interests of the interested parties could be addressed. Manzini (2003) also argued that environmental value could be promoted via the optimization of resource usage between interested parties using the product-service life cycle perspective.

The definition of the PSS may differ from scholar to scholar: It may be defined as a pre-designed system of products, supporting infrastructure and necessary networks that fulfil a user’s needs on the market, have a smaller environmental impact than separate product and services with the same function fulfilment and are self-learning (Centre for Sustainable Design, 2001). A PSS may also be defined as consisting

of tangible products and intangible services, designed and combined so that they are jointly capable of fulfilling specific customer needs (Brandsotter, 2003), or as a solution offered for sale that involves both a product and a service element, to deliver the required functionality (Wong, 2004). All of these definitions share the same core aspect of sustainability. Therefore, in this study, we define the PSS as ‘a system or a business model with ultimate sustainability that, via product and service integration, satisfies consumer needs from both the product and the service perspectives while decreasing environmental damage’.

In the early stages of PSS conceptualization, research of PSS components and their types was actively conducted. Goedkoop (1999) attempted to categorize the PSS according to the product service ratio. The research divides the PSS into four categories based on the type of linkage between the product and the service for functional satisfaction. The first category is the service-attached product (Ps), in which service is based on the product’s life cycle — such as car maintenance service, or after-sales service of a refrigerator. The second category is the product-attached service (Sp), in which a product is delivered in the form of a service — such as an ATM service. The third category is a form of product service system development, and the last category is a type that replaces the entire existing PSS. The proportions of the four categories may vary because of technological and environmental changes.

Mont (2002) attempted a sporadic approach to the existing PSS. Mont pointed out the lack of a unifying understanding of the components comprising the PSS, and suggested the following concepts: (1) the PSS is composed of a product, a service, or a combination of both product and service; (2) a service may occur at the time of sales, such as assistance purchasing a product or the explanation of a product manual; (3) the product usage concept is divided into utility from direct usage and utility from the provider; (4) maintenance and customer support are based on the product’s life cycle; and (5) the PSS includes the disposal stage of a product — recycling, collection, reuse, and so on.

Figure 1. Main and subcategories of PSS (Tukker, 2004)

Tischner et al. (2002) conducted research on the relationship between the PSS and the traditional concept of products and services. The traditional concepts of products and services were placed at the ends of a spectrum, and the PSS was categorized into a product-oriented PSS, a use-oriented PSS, and a result-oriented PSS, according to the position on the spectrum. In a product-oriented PSS, a user or customer owns a product with a renewable service contract or a maintenance and upgrade customer support service. In a use-oriented PSS, a provider owns a product, and usage of the product is shared among customers through various methods. The provider owns the product but has the responsibility to make the product available for usage in return for a certain fee. In a result-oriented PSS, a customer and a provider agree on the required result of the service; however, there is no set product. In this way, the provider can use the minimum amount of human and physical resource to deliver the result agreed upon beforehand.

Tukker (2004) attempts to subdivide the aforementioned three types of PSS, suggesting that the previous study failed to clarify the different environmental and economic characteristics of each type. According to Tukker, the product-oriented PSS is subdivided into (1) product-related service and (2) consultation and advice; the use-oriented PSS is divided into (3) product leases, (4) product lease sharing, and (5) product usage sharing; and the result-oriented PSS is divided into (6) management and outsourcing, (7) service fee per unit, and (8) functional result.

Time use survey

A time use survey is a multi-purpose survey that collects comprehensive data on how a domestic population spends its time. These types of surveys are conducted nationally in various countries including the United States, Japan, Korea, and European countries; however, the survey period, method, and timetable categories differ in different countries. The timetable categories used in this study are subdivided into three based on the location, purpose, and situation of various consumer activities. The first known survey on the use of time is Bevans' research on male workers' use of time in 1913. At the governmental or research institution level, relevant surveys have been conducted since the 1920s in the United States (Cornell University), Russia, and the United Kingdom (British Broadcasting Corporation). In the 1950s, America's CBC used a diary in its survey and report, providing a framework for modern-day time usage surveys. In the United States, time use surveys were conducted on a small scale by individual institutions until 1991, when the U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics developed the national American Time Use Survey (ATUS) in four stages; an annual survey has been conducted since 2003.

The Japan Broadcasting Corporation (NHK) conducted the first time use survey in Japan in 1969, and since 1976, the Statistics Bureau of Japan has conducted a large-scale survey every five years. In Korea, the Rural Development Administration began conducting a time use survey in 1979 to analyze farming households' life patterns. From 1981 to 1995, the Korean

Broadcasting System conducted the National Time Use Survey, and Statistics Korea has been conducting a national time use survey every five years since 1999. An international time use survey was first conducted in the mid-1960s, and Eurostat has conducted these surveys periodically since the 1990s.

RESEARCH METHOD

Structure of consumers' daily life

Before identifying the consumer life domain satisfied by a PSS, this study categorizes the different activities within the consumption life domain. For the time use categorization in this research, we refer to the 2012 ATUS Activity Coding Lexicon, which has the most detailed activity elements. The ATUS Activity Coding Lexicon is a three-tiered classification system with seventeen first-tier categories. Each of the first-tier categories has two additional levels of detail (Bureau of Labor Statistics & U.S. Census Bureau, 2013). We shortened the list of approximately 480 activity elements to 61 activity elements based on the following criteria: (1) the activity element can be satisfied using a product or service, and (2) an individual can autonomously select or utilize a product or service for the activity element. The resulting 61 activity elements are shown in Table 1.

NO.	ACTIVITIES
1	Activities rel. to purchasing/selling/renting real estate
2	Appliance, tool, and toy set-up, rent, repair, & maintenance
3	Arts and crafts as a hobby
4	Attending meetings for personal interest (not volunteering)
5	Attending or hosting parties/receptions/ceremonies
6	Attending, watching sporting/recreational Events
7	Banking
8	Building and repairing furniture
9	Care for animals and pets (not veterinary care)
10	Civic obligations & participation
11	Collecting as a hobby
12	Comparison shopping
13	Computer use for leisure (exc. games)
14	Eating and drinking
15	Exterior cleaning
16	Exterior repair, improvements, & decoration
17	Financial management
18	Food and drink preparation
19	Food presentation
20	Grocery shopping
21	Health-related self-care
22	Heating and cooling(building)
23	HH & personal e-mail and messages
24	HH & personal mail & messages (except e-mail)
25	Hobbies, except arts & crafts and collecting
26	Home security
27	Household & personal organization and planning
28	Interior arrangement, decoration, & repairs
29	Interior cleaning
30	Kitchen and food clean-up
31	Laundry

NO.	ACTIVITIES
32	Lawn, garden, and houseplant care
33	Listening to the radio
34	Listening to/playing music (not radio)
35	Obtaining licenses & paying fines, fees, taxes
36	Participating in sports, exercise, or recreation
37	Personal emergencies
38	Personal/private activities
39	Playing games
40	Ponds, pools, and hot tubs care
41	Purchasing food (not groceries)
42	Purchasing gas(energy)
43	Reading for personal interest
44	Relaxing and Leisure
45	Security procedures rel. to consumer purchases
46	Security procedures rel. to govt svcs/civic obligations
47	Security procedures rel. to professional/personal svcs.
48	Sewing, repairing, & maintaining textiles
49	Shopping, except groceries, food and gas
50	Sleeping
51	Socializing and communicating with others
52	Storing interior hh items, inc. food
53	Telephone calls (to or from)
54	Television and movies (not religious)
55	Tobacco and drug use
56	Traveling/mobility/car
57	Vehicle repair and maintenance
58	Walking / exercising / playing with animals
59	Washing, dressing and grooming oneself
60	Waiting for the activity(including reservation)
61	Writing for personal interest

Table 1. 61 Activities from ATUS Activity Coding Lexicon

Data collection

For this research, we collected 59 actual PSS cases from Korea, the United States, and Europe. Each PSS case includes a product-service business model; pure services and pure products are excluded and only business to consumer (B2C)

services and products are included. Moreover, cases should be well known by consumers' in each case oriented country and the business should be running still now. The cases are selected from PSS researches such as UNEP article and companies' web sites.

Analysis process

In this section, we identify which activity element each of the collected 59 PSS cases satisfies. Following the classifications provided by Mont (2002) and Tukker (2004), the PSS cases are divided into product-oriented, use-oriented, and result-oriented categories, and each case is assigned to a relevant activity element. If one case satisfies multiple activity elements, it is placed under multiple activity elements. The result is then analyzed to identify activities that are (not) satisfied by the existing PSS, and their main method of supply, in order to discover the life domains on which the PSS should focus in the future. Table 2 illustrates the framework used in the analysis.

RESULT

Figure 2 shows a summary of the results. From the analysis, it can be identified that many PSS development attempts have been made for most of the activities within consumers' life structure. This is because, in many cases, PSS development takes place as a form of adding peripheral activities to core activities based on the life cycle perspective. The result also shows that each PSS is involved in an average of 2.6 different activities; this illustrates that the current PSS is focused on a specific activity rather than overall life as a total service. Sports and leisure activities represent the most varied forms of PSS cases; however, there were few PSS cases related to public service, telephone calls, storage, entertainment, private activities, medical activities, janitorial services, and home management. This is because the pure service model better satisfies the aforementioned activities than does the PSS.

PSS CASE		AIR BNB	AMAZON KINDLE	NIKE + IPOD	ZIPCAR	WOOGJIN CDI	I TUNES	DELL	ADIDAS RUNNING SHOP	TOTAL
ACT.	CASE NO.	P001	P002	P003	P004	P056	P057	P058	P059	
	ACTIVITIES / PSS CLASIFICACION	USE	PRODUCT	PRODUCT	USE	PRODUCT	PRODUCT	PRODUCT	USE	
1	Activities rel. to purchasing/selling/renting real estate									0
2	Appliance, tool, and toy set-up, rent, repair, & maintenance (by self)									0
3	Arts and crafts as a hobby									0
4	Attending meeting for personal interest (not volunteering)									0
5	Attending or hosting parties/receptions/ceremonies									0
6	Attending, watching sporting/recreational Events			1						1
7	Banking									0
56	Traveling/mobility/car				1				1	1
57	Vehicle repair and maintenance				1				1	1
58	Walking/exercising/playing with animals			1						1
59	Washing, dressing and grooming oneself						1			1
60	Waiting for the activiy (including reservation)									0
61	Writing for personal interest					1				1
Total		0	0	2	2	1	1	0	2	-
Average of Activities per each PSS Case										-

Table 2. Example Sheet of Analysis Process

Figure 2. Result of PSS Case Analysis Based on Consumer Activity Element

The product-oriented PSS type is most common, accounting for 29 cases; there are 17 use-oriented cases, and a relatively low 13 result-oriented cases. This shows that the PSS still develops in a product-oriented way, and that increases in material flow are still the main focus. For transportation-related activities such as vehicle or bicycle use, the use-oriented type of PSS is most common, and for purchasing activities like shopping, the product-oriented type of PSS is most common because of the inherent nature of the activity. It is not definitive which type of PSS is most efficient for a specific activity; however, an attempt to develop different types to satisfy the same activity may be useful.

In the case of energy-purchasing activities, the car rental activity and the energy-purchasing activity are combined as a use-oriented PSS. This illustrates that it is possible to provide different types of PSS by integrating different activities. The result also showed that the use-oriented PSS type is less accessible for social and communication activities. Social activity must be consolidated when planning a use-oriented PSS.

CONCLUSION

This study analyses some current PSS cases from the consumer life perspective and provides evidence to help in the pursuit of human life — friendly PSS developments. In order to do so, we structuralize consumers' daily lives using the ATUS Activity Coding Lexicon and analyze which life domains are satisfied by current PSS cases based on PSS supply type (product/use/result oriented). The result shows that various existing PSS cases satisfy consumers throughout their overall structuralized life domains. Each PSS case satisfies an average of 2.6 activity elements. This shows that as developers attempt to develop PSS types for various activities, a single PSS cannot act as a total service that satisfies many aspects of consumer daily life. Moreover, each PSS case tends to satisfy one main activity and several additional activities. In other words, integrating different consumer daily activities can be the main source of new ideas for PSS development. Moreover, the result shows that only one type of PSS is currently provided for certain activities, which opens up the possibility to develop different types of PSS to improve these activities.

Current PSS tends to focus on the consumer's needs and user context, which is directly related to the steps on the specific user process. From this point of view, the PSS can meet what people want, but may not really improve their quality of life. Better understanding of the consumers' life structure at the beginning of PSS design stage can be helpful to make the PSS more fitting for human life and closer to sustainability.

But this paper only refers ATUS Activity Coding Lexicon for the analysis, not the actual data of ATUS, so results of the study may suggest limited implication about the consumers' real life structure. In future research, identifying the relationship between specific activities that can be integrated with one another based on ATUS data, and additional analysis of further PSS cases, may facilitate more concrete and empirical proposals.

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EVERYDAY INTERACTIVE-KINETIC ENVIRONMENTS: EXAMPLES IN LATIN AMERICA

FORMATTING GUIDELINES FOR PAPER SUBMISSIONS

Carolina M. Rodríguez, Marta D'Alessandro
Departamento de Arquitectura, Universidad de los Andes, Bogotá, Colombia
✉ cm.rodriguez@uniandes.edu.co, m.dalessandro10@uniandes.edu.co

ABSTRACT

This paper aims to study characteristics present in the development of interactive-kinetic environments in Latin America. For this purpose, a variety of examples are examined. These serve to illustrate the means employed in Latin America to achieve 'high-social' interaction with the appropriate use of available resources. The paper begins with a brief introduction of the existing heritage of interactive-kinetic environments in Latin America and their links to architecture. It supports the argument that architecture and urban space in Latin American can be enriched by generating meaningful and active interactions between people and their environment. A reflection on future horizons on the field concludes the paper.

KEYWORDS: *transformable, kinetic, interactive environments*

BACKGROUND

Interactive-kinetic environments create conditions where the architectural space and/or building fabric can engage in communication with its inhabitants through the use of kinetic and sensory components. In so doing, architecture meets the need of all senses by stimulating tactile, auditory, olfactory and/or visual engagement. This type of interaction relies on both the physical and intangible elements that shape space, instigating a type of architecture that encourages the emergence of new social dynamics. The transformative nature of human interaction, which fuels interactive-kinetic environments, allows the experience of a space to change constantly. This could generate an open type of exchange that goes beyond ordinary participation, where the actors engage in and achieve a deeper and evolving conversation. In this context, traditional architectural systems of production and consumption are altered. Architecture becomes not an end result, but a tool that allows input and output processing. Architects design tools to be used by the inhabitants for the construction of their environment. Hence people are more committed and responsible for the space that they inhabit.

Interactive-kinetic environments have their origins in interactive and kinetic art sculptures and installations of the beginning of the 20th century. One of the earliest examples was

Rotative Plaques Verre, Optique de Précision (1920) by French artist Marcel Duchamp, a sculpture where the viewer was required to initiate a mechanism and stand at a distance in order to see an optical illusion generated by its movement. Further development of kinetic art mobiles and sculptures took place during the 1950s with the work of Russian artists Vladimir Tatlin and Aleksander Rodchenko and American sculptor Alexander Calder. Their experimental endeavours introduced ways to control movement through the use of technological enhancements. Early interactive-kinetic interventions generally remained close to the geometric abstraction at the beginning of the 20th century. Their materialisation was mainly achieved through manually-operated mechanical devices and flexible components. In contrast, the updating of the genre during the 1950s and 1960s tended to overcome geometric and technical boundaries with proposals designed to convey meaning, persuade people, and closely connect them with their surroundings (Oliveras, 2010). Kinetic art conceptually flourished, during this period, allowing the establishment of a more direct and reciprocal relationship between the objects and the observers, as well as between the objects and their environments. European and North American pioneers in this area included Peter Vogel, Nicolas Schöffer, Vassilakis Takis, James Seawright, and Wen-Ying Tsai. Numerous Latin American artists were also at the forefront of the kinetic art movement of this period, amongst others, Antonio Asis,

Martha Boto, Vardanega, Gertrude Goldschmidt, and Gregorio Vardanega. It has been argued that the conceptual background behind kinetic art developments was influenced by different factors in each part of the world. In North America, for example, motion was linked to the dynamicity of trends in the upcoming visual arts, cinema, and television. European endeavours were more driven by technological experimentation with novel mechanisms and materials, whilst Latin American proposals were instigated by utopian ideals of social transformation and progression (Bayon, 1974). This was connected to the arrival of modernity to Latin America, which resulted in numerous changes in all areas and prompted the search for new artistic languages to represent them. Such quests resulted in different types of expressionism; kinetic art being one of the most suggestive.

Parallel to the development of kinetic art, cybernetic theories were taking shape, attempting to explain and propose learning strategies for living organisms and machines. Norbert Wiener in the 1940s (Wiener, 1948), and later on, Gordon Pask during the 1970s (Pask, 1975), argued that living and non-living systems can both have 'purpose', hence it was possible to establish effective communication through an exchange of actions between humans and machines. These ideas lead researchers to believe that the relationship between user and space could constitute a system of continuous feedback in which the spaces may change according to the needs of people. Such beliefs fuelled kinetic art proposals that comprised, not only moving objects actuated by people, but also provided a new platform for social interaction between people and art.

A seminal example was the work of Venezuelan artists Jesus Soto, Carlos Cruz Diez, and Alejandro Otero, who took a revolutionary stand through their creations. They were actively involved in 'Los Disidentes' (The Dissidents) 1945-1950, an artistic group which opposed the political scene of Venezuela, at the time, describing it as regressive and stagnant (*Los Disidentes*, 1950). Their work sought to create new settings in which to integrate moving objects, light, colour, time, and the viewer. In such settings motion was not actuated by mechanical means, but created by the spontaneous participation of the audience. This was the case with Soto's installations entitled *Penetrables*, many of which are still in use. They consist of large prismatic steel structures from which arrays of thin, plastic tubes dangle, and through which observers can walk. Their aesthetic experience covers all senses besides sight, as they can also be touched, smelt, heard and most importantly, lived.

Another influential example for Latin America was the work of the artistic Group GRAV (*Groupe de Recherche d'Art Visuel*) between 1960 and 1968. Argentinean artists Julio Le Parc, Horacio Garcia Rossi, Hugo Demarco, and Norberto Gómez, amongst other artists from Spain and France, founded GRAV in Paris. GRAV's most important contribution was to shift the emphasis from the moving object to its interpretation and experience. The interest was placed on the audience, who was actively involved in the works, as stated in their 1966 manifesto:

We are particularly interested in the proliferation of works which permit of varied situations, whether they engender a strong

visual excitement, or demand a move on the part of the spectator, or contain in themselves a principle of transformation, or whether they call for active participation from the spectator... but this is only a first stage. The second might be, for example, to produce, no longer only the works, but ensembles which would play the part of social incitement, at the same time as liberating the spectator from the obsession with possession (Stiles & Selz, 1996, p. 411).

Over the past two decades, the design of interactive-kinetic environments in Latin America has rapidly advanced in complexity, both theoretically and technically. Its inclusion as a topic of research and experimentation within architectural academic fields is becoming stronger. Sensors and actuators that monitor changes in habitable spaces are becoming widely available. In addition, with the advent of personal computers and technological empowerment to all kinds of people, more dynamic, direct, and real-time control can be achieved. But most importantly, there is a common realisation that technology is not a barrier for creativity and that truly interactive-kinetic environments do not necessarily rely on the complexity of the physical components used, but on the sophistication of the interactive strategy. This is underlined by the argument posed by various authors of a shift from a mechanical paradigm to a biological paradigm in which spaces have the ability to change as circumstances change in a more intuitive and flowing manner (Fox, 2009, p.19).

REINFORCING 'HIGH-SOCIAL'

Contemporary human changing patterns and technologically influenced lifestyles are the driving force behind new developments in interactive-kinetic environments (Fox & Kemp, 2009). As explorations become more theoretically and technically complex, gaps between artists, architects, and engineers are bridged. Very often, the boundaries between disciplines become blurred when merging choreographed motion, digital media and electronics with physical settings. In Latin-America, artists (more than architects or engineers) seem to be leading this integration. An interesting example is the work of the Argentine theatre company *Fuerzabruta* (recently named one of the top most innovative companies in South America). Their productions feature remarkable kinetic devices and great visual and lighting effects, all brought alive by audience participation. In general, the emphasis has been on the high-social aspect of the interventions, regardless of the means used to materialise the interaction, and the physical movement. In other words, the design of the social event takes priority over the type of technical tools employed to achieve it.

Latin America is a region where there is great disparity between extreme poverty and immense wealth, as well as social and political instability. However, there is still a great display of formal and technical creativity, especially in the process of formulating alternative ways to apply available resources. In this context, the appropriate integration of technical means within the design process is a determining factor for their effectiveness. On one hand, relatively high-end technology can

be accessible for the design and production of architecture; although, this technology is not always appropriated for the needs that it is attempting to address and the socio-cultural conditions where it is implemented. On the other hand, there is a growing drive to develop local, more efficient, and self-reliant technologies. This is complemented with design philosophies that fit within fiscal limitations and have the ability to take root and evolve over time. Given these conditions, the challenge is to explore potential intersections between computer-aided design, available materials and resources, new manufacturing processes and traditional crafts. This challenge drives many of the projects featured in this paper.

In some projects, the kinetic-object is used as a facilitator and not as a protagonist for the interaction. Hence, the exploration becomes less ambitious in method and more specific in scope, by using very simple components and unpretentious materials that flavour the project's discourse. This is the paradigm in *Milltütten* (2012), an interactive urban installation by architecture students from the Universidad de Talca, Chile. Its name is a fusion of the Spanish word *mil* (a thousand), and the German word *mülltüten* (bin bag). The installation comprised of six metres high by sixty metres long waving fabric, made from a thousand black bin bags, all knotted together in the corners. Placed at the main entrance of the University of Kassel in Germany, its intention was to expose the wind as the connector integrating the campus to the city, whilst giving another value and meaning to a usually understated material.

Other projects use a range of kinetic and mechanical devices actuated by people's movements. *Solo* (2010) and *Tunnel* (2010), both by Brazilian artists Rejane Cantoni and Leonardo Crescenti (Cantoni-Crescenti), are fitting examples. *Solo* presents a surface formed by a series of interconnected panels, supported on seesaw-type mechanisms which make them unstable. As visitors walk over the surface, the panels swing from side to side, in function of the forces applied to them. Any localised movement produces repercussions on the neighbouring plates, so the entire surface moves creating waves. The purpose behind it is that the audience can interact with the project and between one-another simultaneously.

Tunnel has a similar interactive goal and also uses people's weight to induce motion. This installation is composed of 92 interlinked metal frames, supported on a central beam. As people walk through it the frames oscillate up to five degrees at either side creating undulatory movements across the entire structure. Another very interesting example was *On Space Time Foam* (2012) by Argentinean artist Tomas Saraceno. This project comprised a multi-layered space made from elastic, translucent PVC membranes, covering an area of 400 square metres, and suspended 24 meters above ground level at the *Cubo* space of the HangarBicocca in Milan, Italy. Visitors had the opportunity to access it from above, observe it from below, or penetrate an inflated air cushion formed in between. The different layers of the space were constantly activated by the changes in climate, air pressure, and participation of people. This work was inspired by *El Jardín de Senderos Que se Bifurcan* (The Garden of Forking Paths) (1941) by Argentinean

writer Jorge Luis Borges, a story in which there is no uniform or absolute time, but an infinite series of divergent, convergent, and parallel times. It was also connected to theories of quantum physics, which argue that the universe is structured like foam in which space and time change coordinates. In Saraceno's work, the symbiotic relationship between user and structure was intended as a metaphor for how human interrelations affect each other and the Earth in which we live. Hence, every step unchained a series of reactions modifying the spatial coordinates of other people and also impacting upon a 'parallel universe', represented by the spaces above or below each layer.

The work of Mexican artist Rafael Lozano-Hemmer also embodies the desire to construct not only enjoyable experiences, but also meaningful social interactions and positive reinforcement. *Homografías* (Homographies) (2006/2012), for example, comprises 144 standard white-fluorescent light-tubes hung from 72 robotic fixtures on the ceiling of a habitable space. Each 1.83 metre-long light tube revolves on its central axis using a computer-controlled stepper motor. This is linked to a surveillance tracking system of six panoptic cameras (placed on the ceiling), which detect the presence and position of people in the space. As they move, the light tubes slowly revolve generating different patterns and 'paths of light' that vary in relation to the number of people present and their actions. Every certain period of time, the tubes align forming orthogonal arrangements. Plasma screens of the walls show the tracking systems, informing people about the position of others and their effect on the behaviour of the overall system. The author argues that in many buildings, such as offices, hospitals, factories and prisons, the ubiquitous presence of fluorescent light tube creates a cold experience of functional normalisation. *Homografías* attempts to pervert this perception and offers a plurality of points of contact by generating alternating compositions.

IMPACT ON ARCHITECTURAL AND URBAN SPACE

Unlike other forms of art, interactive-kinetic installations are not suitable for reproduction on paper or digital media, nor can they have a place in a gallery or a museum in the traditional manner. Due to their size and collaborative nature with the audience, they become an integral part of the architectural and urban space. Even though most built examples have been transitory installations, they prove to have a considerable impact on habitable spaces. This suggests that they ought to be considered not just as elements placed in a space, but as architectural components. Ever since their beginnings, the fundamental rationale behind the design of interactive-kinetic environments has been to create an interface between four key ingredients: the user/audience (subject), the kinetic artefact (object), the event (experience), and the hosting space (architecture). Different aspects of interactive-kinetic environments are highlighted according to the emphasis placed on these different ingredients. For example, the complexity of the technical means used to build the kinetic components (em-

phasis on the object); the degree of physical transformation and integration with the surroundings (emphasis on the relationship object-architecture); the type of interactive encounter and the degree of interaction with the audience (emphasis on the relationship object-experience-subject); and the level of response to specific design agendas/problems (emphasis on the relationship object-architecture- subject). In design approaches that reinforce a relationship between the object and the architecture, the character given to the object is of great importance, since it would determine the intensity of the interaction. The object needs to have a certain level of sophistication or ‘intelligence’ in order to engage and sustain communication with the audience. On the other hand, in approaches that use the object/architecture as a medium to instigate and emphasise interaction between people within the audience, the design of the experience takes priority. This experience needs to be compelling and persuasive in order to encourage exchange amongst participants.

An example of the first scenario is *Environmental Noise Interactive Façade (ENIF)* (2009-10), developed at Universidad de los Andes. This façade was fitted with noise sensors that collected audio frequencies from the surrounding environment. In order to make the skin respond to localised noise by physically distorting specific sections of its reflective surface, Input data was managed through micro-controllers programmed with *Wiring*. The experience allowed visitors to visualise alterations in noise levels and reflect on the range of noise pollution in the local environment. Another case is *Fachada* (2012) by Antoni-Crescenti, an interactive-kinetic installation fixed on the main façade of the *Espacio Fundación Telefónica* Building in Buenos Aires, Argentina. The installation is made from 75 thin aluminium strips, which in sequence swivel 90 degrees back and forth. Initially, all strips are placed perpendicular to the façade. When a pedestrian approaches the building its presence is detected by sensors located at the ends of the façade. This starts up a mechanism comprising a short steel plate which slides over a rail at the bottom of the aluminium strips, whilst progressively pushing them into a parallel position to the façade. When the plate has passed, the strips go back to their original arrangement pulled by a weight-driven mechanism. The strips have a matt finish on the inside and a reflective mirror-like finish on the outside. As they move, they reflect the surroundings establishing a dialog between people inside and outside the building. The interaction continuously changes according to the flow of people moving in front of the building and the conditions of the environment that is reflected.

Although most of the examples shown so far in this paper are or were temporary installations proposed by artists, there is a growing interest in the subject between architects and engineers (especially within academia). This suggests that it could only be a matter of time before interactive-kinetic environments could be explored as permanent or more common features of buildings. In addition, there is currently an active debate within the design community, which has raised a range of still unresolved questions. For example: ‘Can interactive-kinetic environments form part of everyday spaces?’; ‘Are all types of interactions suitable for the Latin-American context?’

and, Is the technology used fitting for the local context?’. These questions stirred two explorations, *Guayering* and *Col-orama*, developed at Universidad de Los Andes by two groups of Master students, lead by the first author of this paper. The main drive for these explorations was to ground an interactive-kinetic environment in the internalisation of an existing everyday space. This with the aim of highlighting and enhancing the elements and structures of the environment that often go unnoticed by their constant, daily, and habitual presence. In fact, during the theoretical development of the proposals, it was noted that, although there have been several projects of interactive-kinetic environments located in everyday spaces, much of the experimentation had concentrated on the search for new forms and devices of interaction and movement. However, there has been little exploration of the potential in utilising primary characteristics of customary spaces in order to transform them into interactive-kinetic environments. The two projects, subsequently presented, were designed based on evolutionary patterns of growth and strategies of behaviour that would allow them to adapt to the actions of their inhabitants/actors.

Guayering (2012), named from an adaptation of the Spanish word *guaya* (wire), aimed to augment and mediate human experience, interaction and perception through the use of a temporary envelope that changed the meaning and function of an existing space. The project consisted of an enclosure made from a large white elastic fabric suspended from thirty points, sixteen of which were linked to two mobiles made from rectangular aluminium profiles and steel wire. Each mobile was linked to a pulley and connected to a standard manually-operated crank-mechanism, which allowed people passing by to raise it up or lower it down. During this process, the enclosure progressively transformed increasing or decreasing the size of the inhabited space. Consequently, the level of intimacy and closeness between people was constantly altered. As the space became smaller, inside users could pull on plastic bottles filled with coloured ink that were attached to the fabric. Through this action, the ink progressively tainted the enclosure exposing the degree of interaction between the object and the user. The experience was designed in order to make the audience aware of the impact that their actions may have on others.

The project was monitored for ten days through the collection of quantitative and qualitative data aimed to evaluate the complexity and richness of the observations, associations, and perceptions that the users constructed during their experience. Amongst other things, it was found that certain groups of audiences, such as young children, tended to interact more freely with the space, pushing its physical boundaries to the limit. They appeared not to be intimidated when the space became smaller, forcing them to get closer. University students, instead, used the movable devices as an excuse to communicate with each other through physical or verbal actions. For example, some would make the fabric drop on purpose over their classmates, in order to instigate their reaction. In contrast, some adults only stopped to observe others interacting with the environment.

Figure 1-3. *Guayering*, details of the proposal's components. Photos: Oscar Prieto

Figure 4-6. *Guayering*, Mechanisms used to actuate the mobiles and textile. Photos: Oscar Prieto

Figure 7-11. *Guayering*, interaction during evaluation period. Photos: Oscar Prieto

Colorama (2013) intended to underline an everyday passageway, through the play of light, colour and shadow, whilst empowering pedestrians as active agents of their changing environment and enriching their experience. The project was placed on a highly transited and glass-enclosed bridge that connects two buildings of the University Campus. The bridge frames a privileged view of Bogota's city centre on one side and a prominent view of the Andes Mountains on the other. However, during a primary study of the space it was noticed that people passing by very rarely became aware of or gave importance to these views. Hence, the first objective of the project was to transform the traditional relationships established between people, and the immediate physical context of the bridge, by highlighting the views through spinning coloured elements. Ninety of these elements were placed on both sides of the bridge. Each one was built with four pieces of 36 centimetre-long coloured acrylics forming a swastika paddle wheel. They were designed to be manually rotated, generating changing coloured patterns and lighting effects inside the bridge. The second objective of the proposal was to change the existing

perception of the bridge of being a purely transit space by encouraging people to stop and interact with the environment and with each other. In order to achieve this, the colour paddle wheels were framed by large black board surfaces where people could express themselves through writing or drawing. This interaction built new relationships between passers-by that stopped to write a message or read, add, oppose or discuss someone else's message, which in turn helped to establish an open and evolving communication flow. Day by day the space was enriched and transformed by new interventions. During the monitoring period it was noticed that, in general, the users responded to the proposal as it was originally imagined, by spinning the swastika elements. Many stopped and observed the city through the different colours; others just enjoyed the tactile experience of moving the elements. When pedestrians realised the possibility of writing on the panels, the number of them who stopped inside the project significantly increased. At this point the project began a more drastic transformation, by inciting further, and unexpected, social interaction between participants.

Figure 12-16. *Colorama*, proposal's components. Photos:12,16 Oscar Prieto, 13,14,15 Crystian Melo

Some iconic kinetic interactive environments using advanced technological systems have generated the wrong impression: that in this field there is only room for advanced technology or high economic resources. One of the challenges of *Guayering* and *Colorama* experiments was to demonstrate precisely that it was possible to obtain environments with the desired level of interaction, even without the use of complex or expensive strategies. Undoubtedly the integration of technology in the design of interactive kinetic environments may represent a key component to create a more effective interaction. However, some amongst the more prominent theorists in the field pose a demystification of the role of technology within interaction design. Interaction is not a specific field of computers: 'one can create something interactive yet not hi-tech - likewise one

can create something hi-tech yet not the slightest bit interactive' (Haque, 2006).

NEW HORIZONS

The examples presented here are a tester of the type of interactive-kinetic environments being currently developed in Latin America or by Latin American designers abroad. They represent the aspiration to enhance and mediate a diversity of human encounters through engaging and transformative built environments, where appropriated technology and local technology are very much complementary. A growing interest in the subject makes this a very current, vibrant,

Figure 17-20. *Colorama*, interaction during evaluation period. Photos:17,18 Oscar Prieto, 19 Eduard Romero, 20 Carolina Rodriguez

exiting, and evolving field. This is evident in the increasing support by different organisations and practices, which sponsor events and design competition targeting the development of innovative interactive-kinetic environments. The Young Architects Program (YAP) is an example, launched by CONSTRUCTO together with The Museum of Modern Art (MoMA), which aimed to create new opportunities for talented Latin American architects to think, explore, and improve the quality of collective-use spaces. The project *Water Cathedral* (2012) by GUN Arquitectos, winner of the YAP, illustrates the tendencies developing amongst upcoming new generations. Built in the walled forecourt of Matucana 100, in Santiago de Chile, this intervention formed a dynamic forest of tapered white fabric bags, suspended from steel frames that sway gently, oozing water as people stroll through. This is yet another testimony of Latin-American emerging architecture concerned with providing novel and sensible design solutions, whilst embracing social needs, aspirations and diversity of expression. Various authors argue that Latin America in the new millennium is: “witnessing the passage from a difficult adolescence to a state

of grace and plenitude also visible in economic, social, and political optimism (Ábalos, 2011, p. 16).

In this context, the challenges that designers are presented with include learning from cultural heritage and traditional techniques, and responding to unique cultural and environmental conditions, whilst remaining current and becoming more visible to the outside world. In regards to interactive-kinetic environments, the lack of resources has become, more than a barrier, an opportunity for creativity and innovation that can be applied and openly enjoyed in everyday spaces. In most cases, technology plays a secondary role, mediating between the social and cultural aspects of the interaction, which are the protagonists.

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PATH TO SUSTAINED USAGE: A MODEL FOR LONG TERM EXPERIENCE IN TECHNOLOGICAL PRODUCTS

Hakan Boğazpınar, Yekta Bakırlioğlu, Armağan Kuru, Çiğdem Erbuğ
Middle East Technical University

✉ hbogazpınar@gmail.com, yekta@metu.edu.tr, k.armagan@gmail.com, erbug@metu.edu.tr

ABSTRACT

Happiness is one of the major influences in what makes people use products, and what makes those products an important part of daily life. What drives these aspects, some arisen from personal appraisal and some directly related to the product qualities, are important for designers, as the experiences designers form tend to affect these aspects heavily. Driven from this idea, in this paper, an exploration on the evolution of positive user experience with technological products was conducted. We asked users to think about the technological products they enjoy the most, how their experiences changed over time, and what makes them still use the product. Different qualities regarding their experience were found, some human-related, some product-related, and the relations between these qualities were looked upon further in depth. The result presented itself as a theoretical model to achieve sustained usage of technological products.

KEYWORDS: *positive experience in technological products, happiness in product use, pleasure*

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Technology has commercialized to a point where it is not regarded as a novelty piece, rather a given in products. The products became capable of doing more than what the users need or want, and the market is filled with many different personal technological products in different sizes, shapes, colors, and features. The user is baffled with the excessive amount of possibilities, yet still manages to favor one of them over all others. As an example, the studies show that 48% of product returns happen because of non-technical results and 28% of the those are because the product did not work as expected (Ouden et al., 2006). In that sense, the focus has already shifted from the traditional task-oriented approach of HCI, and the attempt has gone beyond understanding users' functional needs, to understanding the aspects that satisfies users' pleasures (Hassenzahl, 2008).

In the last decade, the user experience became a trend, but also an insufficiently investigated topic due to the lack of empirical studies conducted (Hassenzahl & Tractinsky, 2006). In this sense, Vermeeren et al. (2010, p.521) drew out a comprehensive framework by stating the UX is 'to be generally understood as inherently dynamic given the ever-changing internal and emotional state of a person and differences

in the circumstances during and after an interaction with a product'. As an early attempt, Jordan's (2000) identification of four types of pleasures, namely, *physio-pleasure*, *socio-pleasure*, *psycho-pleasure*, and *ideo-pleasure*, shed light on the understanding of pleasures that arise from the use of technological products. Such an identification can highlight a significant relation between user's holistic perceptions with products. According to Hassenzahl and Tractinsky (2006), inherent emotional states refer to universal human needs that are satisfied by the hedonic aspects of UX, yet do not necessarily have to accommodate functional/pragmatic qualities of the products. Moreover, the empirical studies showed that hedonic and pragmatic qualities both promote the desirability and attractiveness of products (Cila & Erbug, 2008; Hassenzahl, 2003, 2007; Schrepp et al., 2006). Their influence relatively changes in relation to the context of evolution and impulsive orientation of the user (Hassenzahl, 2008).

Currently, user experience literature has evolved from solely understanding the emotions towards products, but has kept the dynamism of emotions and turned those into a long-term positive experience (Desmet & Hassenzahl, 2012). Thus, understanding people's experience in long-term usage can lead designers to turn an experience into a 'happy experience'. The study of Chitturi et al. (2008) showed that the impact of hedon-

ic aspects on customer loyalty is more influential compared to pragmatic aspects of the product in the long term. Contrarily, most of the empirical studies of UX mainly focus on the evaluation of short-term experiences (Vermeeren et al., 2008), and single behavioral episodes that mostly ignore the ever-changing goals and needs of the user (Vermeeren et al., 2010).

CONTINUITY OF POSITIVE EXPERIENCE

Conception of long-term experience was first introduced by Dewey (1938) as continuity of experience. As he stated; each experience is influenced by previous ones and each affects the path of future experiences. Thus, regarding the dependencies that are formed through previous experiences, a user defines a specific *path* about his/her way of doing and experiencing (Dewey, 1938). It is interesting to see that, short-term experiences have significant impact on the overall UX (Forlizzi & Battarbee, 2004) whereas the evaluation of overall UX is basically not a consolidation of individual and short-term experiences (Hassenzahl & Ullrich, 2007). From a parallel perspective; the study of Karapanos et al. (2009) shows that the user's judgmental process is predominated by the utilitarian product aspects such as usability, functionality etc. mainly in the initial stage, however as the authors stated, the hedonic aspects take over in the long run.

The study of Kuru (2013) draws a model to explain the process of sustaining usage for a personal technology in four phases. According to the model, people's 'willingness' and initial goals are essential for leading people to become users. In the early days of usage, people explore the product and 'initial benefits' are expected to be satisfied. Once they feel that 'initial goals' are achieved, in the 'extended benefits' phase, expectations are increased to keep using since the needs of the user change. Finally in the 'adoption' phase, users expect the product to offer more personalized interactions that inspire long-term use.

Similarly, Bodker and Christiansen (2012) investigated the long term UX from the points of micro and macro levels. As they stated; in the micro level the user first adapts and then adopts the product by passing through purpose, tradition, and idiosyncrasy phases. In the purpose phase, the user is initially in a state of anticipation and explores the functions to find use purposes. Tradition is the 'micro level appropriation phase' where the user develops repetitive usage rituals; in other words, the use purposes that were found in previous phase are habitualized. In the idiosyncrasy phase, the user develops particular usages in accordance with their personal desires and needs. Concurrently at the macro level, using capabilities of user are changed. As the usage evolves into different contexts, these context changes alter the user's ways of living. At the macro level, rather than integrating the new product into life, the life of the user expands itself and they get involved in activities that were not previously anticipated.

These current studies show that there is a tendency to study the journey of long-term experience, how the experience and

user's relation with the products evolve over time, from the first moment of encounter to simply becoming a part of every-daily life. On the other hand, what makes people happy with a product can be a source of pleasant and pleasurable experiences (Nicolas et al., 2013).

Our interest in this paper is not to involve a problem-driven research (Desmet & Hassenzahl, 2012), but rather to search for possibilities upon asking users their stories about the products they enjoy. In this manner a study was carried out with the hope of extending our understanding of affecting product-related qualities and affected human-related qualities that inspire sustained usage through product stories, and how these are affecting relationships and positive user experience over time. In short, the study aimed to find out an initial model for understanding the design qualities that are leading sustained usage in technological products. Thus, we will explore these qualities through the following questions: [1] What are the human-related qualities and product-related qualities affecting sustained usage?; [2] What are the relations between human-related qualities and product-related qualities according to use phases; and [3] What is the relation between pleasure in use and human-related qualities? If there is a relation, what are the product-related qualities affecting pleasure in use? The following section outlines the data collection and analysis processes of the empirical study that we conducted to answer these questions.

METHODOLOGY

To better understand the evolution of positive experience in technological product use, we conducted a qualitative research study asking twenty participants to explain their experience with the technological products that they enjoy the most. We interviewed the participants and made structured analysis to find the details of their experience.

Selection of Participants and Products

The study was intended to include users that are actively using at least one technological product for a period of time in order not to face a strong bias in participants. Hence, availability sampling was employed insofar as we requested twenty-five people from our work environment to participate in the study. All of them accepted our request, so twenty of them (ten females and ten males, whose ages ranged from twenty-five to thirty-five) were selected in accordance with our personal judgments about who may contribute significantly to the study in terms of their familiarities to the technological products. In total, of the twenty participants, ten selected smart phones, five selected tablet PCs and the rest selected digital cameras, game consoles, smart TVs, headphones, and laptop PCs as their favorite products.

Data Collection

To uncover the evolution of positive experience with technological products, we conducted semi-structured interviews.

At the beginning, the participants were asked to pick one technological product they enjoyed most according to the experience rather than appearance. They were free to choose whatever technological product they wanted to, regardless of the function of the device. This was considered to indicate the ‘positive user experience’ they have with the product they picked. The interview consisted of six main questions asking: (1) What the product is; (2) What their story with the product is; (3) How they got the product, what their impressions were of it when they got it, and how the relationship between the product and the user changed over time; (4) What the positive and negatives are for the product, and if there should be any changes in it; (5) What kept them using the product over the course of time; and (6) what is next for the product. The average duration of a session was thirty-two minutes.

Data Coding

In order to analyze the collected data, a content analysis method (Krippendorff, 2004) for qualitative gatherings was employed. After all interviews were conducted, a structured qualitative data analysis flow was systematized. The analysis flow of collected data is summarized in Figure 1.

Taking into consideration the aim of the study and the research questions posed, to enrich the comprehension of the empirical manifestation of the study, while increasing the reliability of findings, an inter-rater reliability analysis using the Kappa statistic was performed to determine consistency among raters. A representative sample which includes 106 numbers of coding for 53 lines, and a glossary of terms sheet was prepared by researchers to conduct a pilot test with a

Figure 1. Data analysis flow

PRODUCT RELATED QUALITIES (THE PRODUCT IS...)	
QUALITY	MEANING
Aesthetically Pleasing	Having appealing visual properties
Compatibility	Being able to be used along/with other technological products/services
Connectivity	Being able to be connected to networks
Cost effectiveness	Having a price that seems viable in relation to its properties/features
Customization	Being able to match product features with user needs
Durability	Being able to withstand everyday physical abuse
Ease of Communication	Enabling communication with other people
Ease of Interaction	Offering an easy way to control/communicate with the product
Meaningful Data	Understanding the user and conveying related data in a meaningful way
Mobility	Being easy to carry around and available anywhere
Multi-functionality	Being able to carry out more than one task
Newness	Having technological/new features
Personalization	Offering more than one option to provide features according to user preferences/ desires/etc.
Popularity	Becoming known around
Product expression	Having expressive qualities that make people feel like they belong to a group etc.
Smartness	Being able to learn and act in response to users' needs
Social Enabling	Enabling communication with friends and other people around
Technological competence of product	Having technological features and their appropriateness for tasks
Upgrading (Obsolescence)	Being able to be renewed over time (physically or digitally)
Usefulness	Having features that help people to perform activities
HUMAN RELATED QUALITIES (THE USER)	
Adaptation	Can use product features adapt over a period of time
Change in habits	Can transform/change/modify the habits after acquiring the product

Change of 'Context'	Can do stuff in new/different contexts
Excitement	Feels excited due to the product usage
Familiarization	Becomes aware of what the user can and cannot do with the product
Feeling in-Control	Is sure s/he is controlling what's happening
Habitualization	Makes the product a habitual part of life (including frequent use)
Path Dependency	Carries habits/practices from previous experiences (with similar features) affecting the new experience
Pleasure in Use	Feels pleasure and enjoys using the product/system
Surprise (Disappointment)	Feels unpleasant as a result of the unexpected features, or lack of features

Table 1. Glossary of Terms

coder for observing reliability levels of data analysis flow. The inter-rater reliability for the raters was found to be Kappa = 0.790 ($p < 0.001$). The disagreements were then discussed until an agreement was reached. Still, the Kappa value shows that there is evidence for the repeatability of measurements between coders.

During the analysis, we tried to discover the relations between product-related and human-related aspects of experience. Figure 2 shows a typical coding procedure. In the figure, the green-highlighted phrases indicate the causing product-related qualities, and the green arrows show which product quality they are related to. The blue-highlighted phrases indicate the affected human qualities, and the blue arrows show which human-related quality they are related to.

Figure 2. An example of how coding is done

LINES	CAUSING PRODUCT QUALITIES	+/-	RELATED PRODUCT PROPERTY	AFFECTED HUMAN QUALITIES	+/-	REASON / RESULT	TIME
To be honest, I don't think it's possible for us not to be aware of this product → not to see or hear about it — since the day that it was released.	popularity	+	Product's popularity	familiarization	+	To see or hear about the product continuously	Before use
But the facilities that it provides are not the kind that I can be unaware of. — I've been using it for almost 4 months.	usefulness	+	Facilities that the product provides for usage	sustained usage	+	Using the product for four months	Before use
To receive it as a present unexpectedly when I really need it made me incredibly happy.	usefulness	+	The fact that she thinks she needs the product	surprise	+	Receiving unexpectedly as a gift.	Before use

Table 2. Three examples of comments and how they are coded on the Excel sheet

By giving each text unit a number to relate units with a pre-determined theme, all text units were identified with at least one thematic code in Microsoft Windows Office Excel 2007 sheet, as displayed below. In order to sort human-related qualities and understand their relations with product-related qualities, we named the product phases that those qualities were mentioned, as before acquiring, learning phase, mastery phase, and stabilized use phase.

RESULTS

Upon coding data, the analysis is done by counting the number of times the codes are mentioned and by counting the number of times a product-related quality and a human-related quality is mentioned together. On the table below, the left column is the list of product-related qualities and the top row is the list of affected human-related qualities (Table 3).

Qualities are sorted according to the times they were mentioned. Also, the relations between product-related and human-related qualities are highlighted according to the number of times they were mentioned together. According to the data, the most important human related qualities were pleasure in use, habitualization, change of context, path dependency, familiarization, adaptation, and change in habits.

Using these numbers, a holistic picture of the experience was figured out by covering both the human and product related qualities of experience (Figure 3). The visualized four-stage model explains the phases of positive experience with the presentation of technological products. By digging into the interview data, these phases were named as before acquiring, learning, mastery and post-mastery. We used our data to explain these phases in detail, therefore we separated the human-related and product-related qualities in our initial model.

In our model (Figure 3), the phases are represented as gray outlines encapsulating the human-related qualities dominant within them. Green lines indicate a parallel affect between human-related and product-related qualities, while red ones indicate an opposite relation. The size of the circles and squares are decided according to the number of times they were mentioned, and the thickness of lines indicates the number of times they were mentioned in relation.

This comprehensive picture shows that all phases are affected by similar product-related qualities (i.e. newness, mobility, multi-functionality, usefulness, ease of interaction, personalization, technological competence of product, and connectivity). In this figure, human-related qualities up to sustained usage were represented as steps towards it, yet we do not claim that it needs to be in such step-by-step fashion. We will discuss this idea in detail in the following sections.

	Ease of Interaction	Mobility	Novelty	Tech. Comp. of Product	Connectivity	Personalization	Usefulness	Multi-functionality	Aesthetically Pleasing	Durability	Customization	Social Enabling	Ease of Communication	Upgrading (Obsolescence)	Popularity	Compatibility	Product expression	Smartness	Cost effectiveness	
Pleasure in Use	30	21	7	55	11	5	32	7	19	22	5	11	9	8	1	10	1	3		257
Habitualization	13	19	2	3	22	21	6	11	2	1	2	6	3	1		3		1		116
Change of 'Context'	3	15	1		16	11	4	12		1		1	1			1				66
Path Dependency	17	2	26	2	2	4	4	4		2				2			1			66
Familiarization	3		26	1	2		1		1		4				15		1		1	55
Adaptation	8	2	6	1	6	12	4	3	3	1	4	1	1		1			1		54
Behaviour Change	5	11	1	5	8	5	3	7			2	2	1	1		2				53
Sustained Usage	7	7	2	1	3	9	7	4			2		2	3	1	1	1			50
Feeling In-Control	13	1	1	3	2	4	1	5	1		4		1	2						38
Excitement	1	1	6	2		1	3	1	3					1	1		3		1	24
Surprise (Dissappointment)	2			4	2		6		2		1		1	1			1	1		21
	102	79	78	77	74	72	71	54	31	27	24	21	19	19	19	17	8	6	2	

Table 3. The relations between human-related and product-related qualities

Figure 3. The relations between human-related and product-related qualities according to use phases

Phase One: Before acquiring the product

Acquisition of a product, while having its own dynamic factors affecting the decision, the anticipation of a similar-to-the-previous experience almost never changes. That's why *path dependency* seems to be the only appropriate human-related quality dominant in this phase, backed up by the data collected (Figure 4).

As an example, Participant ten indicated regarding listening to music experience on her MP3 player and on her smart phone.

...You just put the song and it goes on. Okay, you have the option to shuffle on the phone too, but I feel like my MP3 player has a simpler interaction... I mean I know I have the option of downloading some music to my phone then listen if I want to, but no... I don't even do that. I always use my MP3 player to listen to music...

Although there is no pragmatic reason for her not to use the phone as an audio player, due to the *path dependency* of previous experiences, she refuses to use the music player feature on her phone. The majority of interviewees explained that their early experiences with negative expressions were due to the habits and practices that have developed from previous product experiences with similar features. They indicated that, product newness and lack of familiarization resulted in a negative user experience in the form of a mental barrier we call 'path dependent behavior'.

Upon this, reasoning behind the path-dependent behavior manifests as the formation of a mental barrier that arises from the *newness* and unfamiliarity of newly acquired technology that needs first to be broken and then re-established with the new experience. In other words, the newness of the

Figure 4. Qualities relations in Phase One

product will always support path dependency; as the product is new, the user does not totally accept this new product, but rather depends on the paths of previous experience. Thus, affecting product-related qualities such as *ease of interaction* and *usefulness*, actually work against it.

On the other hand, the most effective product-related quality that helps to break path dependency is *ease of interaction*. The break down is being realized when the user finds a way to interact with the device in a more comfortable way. As an example, Participant nine mentions the product-related qualities that helped break path dependency as follows:

...I can say that I am a game-addicted person, I was always playing little flash games on my laptop. I remember the first days with my tablet, I had some difficulties to find it a purpose, I mean, what I was going to use it for? My phone works great for checking e-mails, social networks and other stuff. Then of course, I dug through the application store and found some games that are good enough to keep me glued to the screen. Playing on touch-screen with gestures is definitely more fun compared to pressing some buttons. I mean, first it was a device that I'd spend my spare time with, but then it turned into something different. Now I continue my life in the time that's left from it ...

Phase Two: Learning Phase

Learning phase of the product is about exploring the product, and understanding its capabilities on the micro-level (Figure 5). This phase is where the user finds his or her purposes for using it. Thus, *familiarization* and *adaptation* surfaced from the data as the dominant human-related qualities.

...Tablet was my first smart product, that's why I experienced some difficulties while using, at the beginning due to my lack of knowledge; it took some time to get used to having it in my life. First I've experienced serious problems while getting used to the interface. What I mean by the problems related to interface is that it was my first touch screen experience (Participant 3)

Figure 5. Qualities relations in Phase Two / Learning phase

As can be expected, *newness* of the technological product heavily works against the process of being familiar with it. Looking at the figure above, it can be perceived that *familiarization* and *adaptation* are consequent qualities, yet, they may concurrently occur within the learning phase. While having uncomplicated interaction with the device, *personalization* opportunities, being always connected to the networks and usefulness appears as the most effective product-related qualities at this stage. It is interesting to see that there are no relations between being *mobile* and *familiarization*, even though most of the products that are talked about are mobile devices.

Phase Three: Mastery Phase

Mastery phase of the product is the decision point, in which the user either quits using the product or makes it a part of his/her daily life (Figure 6). Due to the structuring of this research, the participants have already passed the decision point and held onto their beloved products. Thus, we had the chance to shed light upon the dominant human-related qualities in the mastery stage.

Change in context, *change in habits* and *habitualization* are the human-related qualities dominating the mastery phase. *Change in context* is related to acquiring the ability to perform actions within different contexts and/or discovering new ways to perform routines as a result of the acquired technological product. Consequently, this human-related quality is affected mostly by a combination of *multi-functionality*, *connectivity* and *mobility*. To clarify the statement, expression of interviewee, Participant 12 can be given:

...when I need to write a business agreement - and you can understand how boring it is from its name - it means I have to sit at my table getting bored for approximately one and a half hours. On the other hand, I can write the same agreement in open air while drinking my coffee with my tablet and my boring agree-

Figure 6. Qualities relations in Phase Three / Mastery phase

ment writing session turns into a pleasant experience. What I think is; it provides an opportunity for me to discover different aspects of my job beyond discovering the different aspects of the product.

Change in habits requires a newly introduced ability for the user, affecting the way s/he performs certain actions as a result. The surprising result on affecting product-related qualities is that *change in habits* is mostly affected by *mobility*, followed by *connectivity* and *multi-functionality*. Though, performing several actions (i.e. multi-functionality), connected to the internet (i.e. connectivity), in an easy manner (i.e. ease of interaction) present themselves as important affecting qualities. Being able to carry the device (i.e. mobility) that can carry out these actions surfaced as the dominant factor. Quoting the interviewee Participant nine:

... Normally I would never watch TV, but thanks to my tablet, I have started to watch. Because I can watch whatever I want, even foreign shows or series, wherever I want. Also it enabled me to reach and subscribe the journals that I could never reach, again thanks to the tablet, now I am reading more than I used to...

Finally, *habitualization* seems to be the most dominant human-related quality in the mastery phase. This quality suggests the product becomes a frequently used part of the user's life. While *mobility*, *multi-functionality* and *connectivity* majorly affect this human-related quality as well, *personalization* and *ease of interaction* seem to be important product-related qualities affecting *habitualization*. Interviewee Participant 3 exemplifies this, stating:

By then, John (her son) was recently born, and turning on the computer to stay in touch or going through newspapers to catch up with the news was quite a hassle. Consequently, I started to use this smartphone more frequently, since it was a ready-at-hand source, I could easily check my e-mails; look up the news, etc. Now, I always use my smartphone for these kinds of activities.

The results show that, all these human-related qualities dominant in the mastery phase are mainly affected by mobility, connectivity, and multi-functionality. In addition to these, personalization and ease of interaction present themselves as affecting habitualization majorly as well. These results should be studied further in order to understand how and why mobility has such an important role in changing habits.

Phase Four: Post-Mastery Phase

The post-mastery phase is the use phase during which the product is totally embedded into the users' lives, owning its purpose, becoming a habit — or rather an integral part. The human-related quality in this phase is *sustained usage*, in other terms, what kept users using this product with such positive experiences. *Sustained usage* is affected by all the product-related qualities affecting the use phases, as can be seen below (Figure 7). Participant 7 expresses this *sustained usage* quality as follows:

You know, nobody thinks any other device than a phone to make calls. My smartphone has transformed into a device that I use to plan my days, to check my e-mails, to follow my social networks, to find addresses – other than making calls. In time, my relationship with my smartphone stabilized, I cannot say that I discover anything new on it after 2.5 years. But I can say, if my smartphone is taken away, I may get cut off from the people, the world. Hell, I may even get lost in my own city!

In relation, post-mastery stage is where sustained usage is achieved and is affected by all product-related qualities simultaneously. However, the way these qualities affect sustained usage is also explained as a result of passing time, upon passing through the human-related qualities before it. This may also suggest that sustained usage is the accumulating result of the human-related qualities in previous phases..

Figure 7. Qualities relations in Phase Four / Post-mastery phase

Figure 8. Pleasure in Use throughout use phases and its affecting product-related qualities

Pleasure in Use as a separate human-related quality

In this study, pleasure in use is defined as the positive experiences that arise while using the product. For that reason, it is used as an umbrella term, which includes hedonic qualities (e.g. happiness, fun, joy, etc.). This decision for the study — to use ‘pleasure’ as an umbrella term — was made considering all different types of hedonic qualities and their insignificant effects on the product use phases individually (i.e. physio-, socio-, psycho-, ideo-pleasures). Consequently, pleasure in use was mentioned as the most among all human-related qualities and it does not belong to any use phase, but

rather presents itself in every use phases. Considering its unique position in this study, the graph below was developed (Figure 8).

In this study, *pleasure in use* seems to be affected the most by *ease of interaction*, *technological competence of product* and *usefulness*. On the other hand, different product-related qualities (i.e. aesthetically pleasing, durability, social enabling) presented themselves as significantly affecting pleasure in use, but not the other human-related qualities. This result is interesting in the sense that pleasure in use requires these three product-related qualities on top of the pragmatic human-related qualities.

The distribution of pleasure in use among product use phases is important as well, since it peaks in the mastery phase and falls back in post-mastery level. This may suggest that, the peak in pleasure in use through the mastery phase may lead towards sustained usage in the post-mastery level. We propose that, in order to understand this relation between pleasure in use and sustained usage as human-related qualities, further studies should be conducted.

Relations between Product-related Qualities

Ensuring one product quality cannot mean to ensure a success of the product, therefore the product qualities should work together to create intended user experience (Crilly et al., 2008). Upon the analysis of data, it was found important to search for correlations between product-related qualities in the pursuit of grouping these qualities. For this, the Pearson Correlation test was used in order to determine whether there are significant correlations between product-related qualities ($p < 0.05$). The results presented below (Table 4) indicate the significantly correlated qualities (highlighted in black).

Among these qualities, 'newness' presented itself as having a negative correlation with the other product-related qualities. This also shows why 'newness' is generally negatively affecting the human-related qualities. According to this data, the product-related qualities can be mapped according to their correlations to find out the groupings in between them.

Results indicate that 'social enabling', 'durability', and 'aesthetically pleasing' are correlated with each other and these three are also highly correlated with 'technological competence of the product', 'usefulness', and 'ease of interaction'. In relation to our previous findings, we can say that this group affects pleasure in use in general.

The second grouping presents itself due to the correlation between 'mobility', 'multi-functionality', 'ease of interaction', and 'connectivity'. This group affects the mastery phase, as can be seen in previous sections. Another linear grouping occurs between 'personalization', 'connectivity', 'multi-functionality', and 'ease of interaction', which affect the learning phase.

DISCUSSION

Upon analysis of the collected data, an initial model for the path to sustained usage was developed (Figure 10). This path does not suggest the way to design and produce products that achieve sustained usage, but rather shows the common qualities that are observed for the products that achieved it.

In this model, the outer circle indicates the product-related qualities (i.e. *ease of interaction, multi-functionality, connectivity, personalization, mobility*) affecting the path the most throughout the use phases (i.e. *before acquiring, learning, mastery, post-mastery*). The inner yellow circle shows the

	Ease of Interaction	Mobility	Newness	Tech. Comp. Of Prod.	Connectivity	Personalization	Usefulness	Multi-functionality	Aesthetically Pleasing	Durability	Social Enabling
Ease of Interaction		,475	,090	,855**	,130	-,030	,873**	,107	,847**	,881**	,806*
Mobility	,475		-,641	,582	,826*	,473	,625	,832*	,545	,562	,813*
Newness	,090	-,641		-,085	-,604	-,630	-,172	-,669	-,083	-,043	-,298
Tech. Comp. Of Prod.	,855**	,582	-,085		,137	-,208	,980**	,112	,980**	,991**	,879**
Connectivity	,130	,826*	-,604	,137		,777*	,184	,898**	,165	,141	,540
Personalization	-,030	,473	-,630	-,208	,777*		-,086	,647	-,124	-,188	,215
Usefulness	,873**	,625	-,172	,980**	,184	-,086		,172	,969**	,982**	,879**
Multi-functionality	,107	,832*	-,669	,112	,898**	,647	,172		,075	,121	,411
Aesthetically Pleasing	,847**	,545	-,083	,980**	,165	-,124	,969**	,075		,983**	,885**
Durability	,881**	,562	-,043	,991**	,141	-,188	,982**	,121	,983**		,862**
Social Enabling	,806*	,813*	-,298	,879**	,540	,215	,879**	,411	,885**	,862**	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Tabla 4. Correlations between Product-related qualities

Figure 10. Path to sustained usage

changes in pleasure in use throughout the use phases and product-qualities affecting it additionally (i.e. *technological competence of product, usefulness, aesthetically pleasing, durability, social enabling*). This path suggests a continuous cycle of use phases, as the new user experience results in sustained usage, it also creates its own path dependency for the next user experience.

As opposed to studying just the experience of the user with the technological product, we suggest that the technological product experience is first confronted with people's previous experiences with a similar product, and achieves its own dependency through sustained usage (Dewey, 1938). Later on (i.e. *learning phase*) the user actually realizes the possibilities the product offers (i.e. *familiarization*) and its effects on his/her daily life (i.e. *adaptation*). While ease of interacting with the product, its ability to perform various tasks and its intermediary role for connecting to various networks are fundamental to breaking such an attachment to previous experiences, fitting to the users' preferences/desires/etc. also supports this detachment. Upon this detachment from previous experience and adoption of the new (i.e. *mastery stage*), changing the previous habits of the user (i.e. *change in habits*), extending the experience toward new and previously not-possible contexts (i.e. *change of context*), and becoming a part of the daily life (i.e. *habitualization*) witnesses a simultaneous peak in pleasure in use, which may require additional product-related qualities (i.e. *technological competence of product, usefulness, aesthetically pleasing, durability, social enabling*). It is only after this (i.e. *the post-mastery phase*), the product achieves sustained usage and achieves a dependency towards a future novelty.

The model presented here is different from the models of Kuru (2013), and Karapanos et al. (2009), in the sense that our model takes into account previous experience effects

on the new experience and the changes in pleasure in use throughout the use-phases. This conclusion in our model is rather similar to the model of Bodker et al. (2012) regarding the macro level of user experience in the sense that the user's life expands with the product, rather than the product being integrated to it. Achieving sustained usage suggests becoming an integral part of the user's life, and thus the newly formed dependency towards it. Ours is also different from other models in the sense that we tried to explain each phase of experience with product and human related qualities from which the designers can further interrelate while designing.

In the light of these, we suggest that designers of future technological products can benefit from our model, especially when innovative products that challenge existing technological products are in question. Adoption of a product and achieving sustained usage include multi-dimensional and complex relations between various qualities, human and product-related. Our model simply presents how these relations are formed, in an affecting-affected fashion, so that designers can build upon it for future technological projects.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we construct an initial model to understand how a technological product surpasses the dependency to previous experiences and how it achieves a dependency of its own, through sustained usage. We stated that sustained experiences with technological products involve complex relations between affecting product-related and affected human-related qualities, while established on certain qualities. We presented an initial model to simply explain the relations between those qualities. We believe that our model can contribute to the literature as it discusses how people have experienced personal technological products, and what led them to have positive experiences with those.

We think that the model that we have presented in this paper can be a starting point for further investigation of the relations between human and product related qualities in each phase of experience. For further studies, this initial model should be further investigated in detail by researching upon how these product-related qualities affect these use-phases individually. For example, this path to sustained usage sheds light upon the relation between 'mobility' and 'habitualization' having a strong relation. Looking back at the interviews, they generally selected mobile devices to talk upon as well. This needs to be closely studied in order to better understand how and why there is such a strong relation.

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AFFECTIVE TIMELINES TOWARDS THE PRIMARY-PROCESS EMOTIONS OF MOVIE WATCHERS: MEASUREMENTS BASED ON SELF- ANNOTATION AND AFFECTIVE NEUROSCIENCE

Marko Radeta, Zhabiz Shafeyoun and Marco Maiocchi
SIP Lab | Studies on Interaction and Perception | Design Department, Politecnico di Milano
✉ marko@siplab.org, zhabiz@siplab.org, marco@siplab.org

ABSTRACT

The economic success of a movie depends on audience satisfaction and on how much they are emotionally engaged while watching it. Our research is related to the identification of such kinds of emotions felt by movie watchers during screening movie screening. We endorse the model of 7 Primary-process emotions from Affective Neuroscience (SEEKING, PLAY, CARE, FEAR, GRIEF, RAGE and LUST) and ask subjects to watch 14 movies and match them with these 7 emotions. We provide a self-annotating application and reveal "Affective Timelines" of clicks with arousal scenes. We verify that it is possible to discriminate movie watchers' emotions according to their self-annotation by obtaining 0.51 - 0.81 range of accordance in annotating 14 movies and comparing them with the authors of this study. These timelines will be matched with physiological sensors in future research.

KEYWORDS: *Affect Annotation, Primary-process Emotions, Movie Watchers, Movie Analysis, Affective Computing.*

INTRODUCTION

Influencing the emotions is a key factor in satisfying a movie audience and for the overall success of the movie. Movies are art-forms that involve affective, perceptual and intellectual activity (Metz, 1991). Recent years demonstrate a growth in movie affective analysis. The field of affective multimedia content analysis demonstrates several methods to represent the range of emotions experienced by movie watchers (Kang, 2003; Hanjalic and Xu, 2005; Wang and Cheong, 2006; Arifin and Cheung, 2007; Xu, Jin and Luo, 2008; Zhang, Tian, Jiang and Huang, 2008; Zhang, Huang, Tian, Jiang and Gao, 2008). Studies in emotion tracking in movies show that most researchers focus on classifying large movie segments to a small number of distinct categories. In all cases, research has focused on narrow domains, such as specific movie genres, e.g. thrillers, cartoon for kids, love stories, and so on.

On the other hand, emotion tracking and annotation has gained popularity and has been used in numerous studies.

(Malandrakis et al, 2011) used supervised learning techniques for continuous time emotion tracking in movies for the first time. Their study used 12 30-minute movie clips where 7 volunteers had to annotate experienced emotions in a valence-

arousal scale by using the FEELTRACE (Cowie, 2000) emotion annotation tool. Participants viewed the films and, in real-time, annotated their emotional responses by moving the mouse pointer on a square two-dimensional area representing the valence-arousal emotional space. The results from their study contributed to a database of movie emotions in which the best emotion obtains over 50% for high arousal values.

A recent study by Zhang et al. used machine learning and algorithms to depict 13 arousal (e.g. music tempo) and 9 valence features (e.g. brightness) of 4000 movie segments. The performance of their algorithms was 60% accurate (Zhang et al. 2009).

In terms of visualization, there has been an increase in visualizing movie emotions due to increasing movie production. In general, scholars wish to facilitate movie browsing by categorizing their prevailing emotions. In one of their research papers, the scholars proposed the iFelt web interface system (Oliveira, 2011) and in particular, the Emotional Wheel, to catalog, access, browse and visualize movies and movie scenes based on participants' emotional properties and impact. Her study used 10 participants and found that 90% of subjects were visibly enjoying the exploration of timelines. This study inspired us to further pursue how to visualize the emotions.

Emotions captured from facial expressions can be seen in studies with 90% successful tracking (McDuff, El Kaliouby, and Picard, 2011). Their study used a corpora and made it plausible to match emotions for more than 290 videos.

This research was based mostly on short movie scenes shown for the participants in single screenings. Also, most of the research was based on diverse models such as arousal-valence and basic emotions model proposed by Ekman (1992) - happiness, sadness, surprise, fear, anger and disgust. These emotions are used both in movie contents and on users' annotated emotions. To the best of our knowledge, to date, no studies have been undertaken based on an Affective Neuroscience model and involving affective annotations. Our study will use users' annotation in the quest for Primary-process emotions in movie watchers.

In general, the question of how emotions should be modeled is still being contested. Researchers commonly accept the AV (arousal/valence) model. Besides the importance of two-dimensional emotional analysis, our paper is based on modeling proposed by Affective Neuroscience due to its rigorous approach in identifying key emotions. Namely, an internal status of all mammals is a way to increase the survival capacity during the species' evolution and only 7 emotional systems can be recognized: SEEKING, PLAY, CARE, LUST, FEAR, GRIEF and RAGE. In particular, Panksepp (1998) measured and clinically verified these emotions to specific neurotransmitters, exact brain areas and behaviors. Notably, in his research, Ekman's proposed that the emotion "surprise" has not been identified at all as an emotion. Although characterization of emotions by physiological patterns still has some limitations regarding the differentiation of emotions from physiological signals (Rainville et al. 2006), we embrace this model as an intrinsic one as Panksepp argues that emotions are all subcortical (Panksepp, 2010). We can suppose that the neocortex will play a key role in the interpretation of emotions by different cultures and diverse ethical standards; however, these 7 basic emotions are the same across all mammals. The focus of this study will not be on time-consuming neuroscientific analysis. Our aim is to set up a benchmark of Primary-process emotions in movies, which will be evaluated with physiological sensors in future

studies. Further, we contribute with the usage of full-length movies for the purpose of allowing more natural timing for experiencing specific emotions. We should point out that our research also includes categorical labeling for the classification of both movie scenes as well as for a person's self annotation moments in time. However, we believe that our future studies will improve with the differentiation of emotions from physiological signals.

METHODOLOGY

In this section, we explain the (i) establishment of our ground truth - how we create a benchmark of emotions; and (ii) application setup (used to measure emotions felt by movie watchers and compared with authors' emotion agreement).

Establishing the Ground Truth

The analysis was carried out in a multicultural environment with researchers from Serbia (male), Iran (female) and Italy (male). Our study analyzed 16 movies, of which 2 were discarded due to the disagreement among authors (several scenes showed opposite emotions of a kind - e.g. CARE/GRIEF). This left 14 movies for analysis. We categorized movies according to our assumption that a movie can have one prevailing emotion (Table 1).

Two authors watched all movies and had the task to assign emotions which were felt during each scene. For each movie, we extracted scenes according to normal changes in the film (e.g. change of surrounding, a dialogue that evolves into a fight, etc.). For each scene, we extracted the length of seconds and assigned to it a prevailed emotion that each author felt (e.g. for a scene where a couple is passionately kissing, authors most probably annotated the scene as LUST). At the end of scene annotation, authors compared their results and verified the accordance rate expressed in mean value. Our threshold was that each author had the same or same kind of emotion assigned per scene (e.g. either both PLAY, or one PLAY and the other CARE which could be matched as they are both positive emotions).

Figure 1. Mean value and authors' accordance of felt emotion per scene.

Movie: *Nine 1/2 Weeks* by Adrian Lyne. With Mickey Rourke, Kim Basinger (1986)

DOMINANT EMOTION HYPOTHESIS	TITLE	DURATION	TOTAL SCENES	MAX SCENE DURATION	AVERAGE SCENE DURATION
SEEKING	Psycho	1:48:25	59	0:07:26	0:01:52
SEEKING	Birds	1:54:36	113	0:04:25	0:01:00
PLAY	Singin' in the Rain	1:42:39	97	0:05:14	0:01:04
PLAY	Bambi	1:07:40	43	0:06:39	0:01:34
CARE	Pretty Woman	1:59:37	78	0:07:51	0:01:30
CARE	I am Sam	2:12:18	116	0:04:58	0:01:07
FEAR	Night of the Living Dead	1:32:42	57	0:07:01	0:01:43
FEAR	Saw	1:43:12	66	0:04:35	0:01:33
GRIEF	Bitter Moon	2:19:05	104	0:03:59	0:01:21
GRIEF	Dancer in the Dark	2:14:27	94	0:06:15	0:01:27
RAGE	Incident	1:39:31	40	0:35:50	0:02:24
RAGE	Schindler's List	3:06:54	183	0:05:06	0:01:02
LUST	9 1/2 Weeks	1:57:03	91	0:04:43	0:01:18
LUST	Blue is the Warmest Color	2:52:57	106	0:07:57	0:01:39
	sum	28:11:06	1247	Mean	0:01:28
	avg	2:00:48	89	-1sd	0:01:05
				+sd	0:01:51

Table 1. Total annotated movies performed by Authors (2) and Subjects (1 main +3 appearing in three sole movies)

A typical example of authors' agreement can be seen in Figure 1. In this particular movie, we observe an "Affective Timeline" where the X axis is the sequence of scenes (same length) and the Y axis is the intensity (scenes calculated in seconds). This suggests that the higher the peak, the longer the scene and that a specific scene presented an unambiguous emotion.

In the next step, we categorized movies into 3 types:

- **Unequivocal Emotion Movie** - a movie in which a single emotion is dominant above all other emotions. Our thresholds were that the average agreement rate among all authors with respect to: a) a prevalence of any emotion above SEEKING; b) a prevailing emotion has to be at least 50% higher in intensity than other emotions (excluding SEEKING). A typical example can be observed in the figures below. This chart depicts the prevalence of PLAY on SEEKING by more than 30% (as well as more than 50% on CARE, RAGE and LUST emotions found in this movie). In this case, GRIEF, FEAR and a neutral state were considered marginal by all authors as they did not appear in the scenes throughout the movie at all.

Figure 2. PLAY - Singing in the Rain by Stanley Donen.

With Gene Kelly, Donald O'Connor (1952)

Figure 3. RAGE - The Incident by Larry Peerce.

With Victor Arnold, Robert Bannard (1967)

Figure 4. GRIEF - Dancer in the Dark by Lars von Trier. With Björk, Catherine Deneuve (2000)

Figure 5. PLAY - Bambi by James Algar. With Hardie Albright, Stan Alexander (1942)

Figure 6. CARE - I am Sam by Jessie Nelson. With Sean Penn, Michelle Pfeiffer (2001)

Figure 7. FEAR - Night of the Living Dead by George A. Romero. With Duane Jones, Judith O'Dea, Karl Hardman (1968)

- Bridging Emotion Movie** - SEEKING is used to trigger other dominant emotions. Our threshold was similar to the previous case where the prevailing emotions should be 50% more intense than other emotions. A typical example is depicted in Figure 10 below. It is clear to note the dominance of GRIEF on other emotions. We believe that SEEKING in this movie was mostly used to correlate with GRIEF. This is in accordance with Panksepp's argument (Panksepp, 2010) that SEEKING is the mother of all emotions and can be used to trigger all remaining ones. We should note an exception, that although the authors' agreement rate for movie number 11 (see Table 1) is mainly GRIEF, we consider this movie LUST-dominant because it contained a higher number of scenes of sexual activity than scenes with notable grief.
- Two of a Kind Emotion Movie** (including SEEKING and two major dominant emotions). Our threshold was again as in previous cases that a prevailed emotion should be 50% higher in intensity than other emotions. An example can be seen in Figures 14 and 15 below. FEAR and GRIEF are indeed dominant over other emotions where SEEKING was used to augment or diminish FEAR and GRIEF scenes.

Figure 8. LUST - Nine 1/2 Weeks by Adrian Lyne. With Mickey Rourke, Kim Basinger (1986)

Figure 9. CARE - Pretty Woman. Directed by Garry Marshall. With Richard Gere, Julia Roberts (1990)

Figure 10. GRIEF - Bitter Moon by Roman Polanski. With Hugh Grant, Kristin Scott Thomas (1992)

Figure 11. FEAR - Psycho by Alfred Hitchcock. With Anthony Perkins, Janet Leigh, Vera Miles (1960)

Figure 12. FEAR - Birds by Alfred Hitchcock. With Rod Taylor, Tippi Hedren, Suzanne Pleshette (1963)

Figure 13. LUST - Blue is the Warmest Color by Abdellatif Kechiche. With Léa Seydoux, Adèle Exarchopoulos, Salim Kechiouche (2013)

Figure 14. FEAR-GRIEF - Saw by James Wan. With Cary Elwes, Leigh Whannell (2004)

Figure 15. GRIEF-RAGE - Schindler's List by Steven Spielberg. With Liam Neeson, Ralph Fiennes, Ben Kingsley (1993)

Application Setup

To verify our ground truth, we designed and developed a desktop (Win 32, used in research) and mobile (Android, in progress) application - available at <http://siplab.org/Emotions.rar> - and instructed the movie watcher in how to use them. Throughout the present research, subjects used only the desktop application which was switched on next to the window with movie. The main motivation in designing this

application was to try to collect self-annotated emotions as unobtrusively as possible so participants could be enjoying the movie as much as possible. Below are examples of the application's user interfaces.

Subjects were clicking on emotions during 14 movies.

Our main movie watcher was a 29 year-old Polish female who was fond of movies. She was provided with an explanation of the definition of 7 Primary-process emotions followed by an

example. Further, we demonstrated how to use the application by performing basic tests such as reset function, seeing the statistics, finding the location of data file, etc. We instructed the movie watcher to click/tap on an emotion when she felt one while watching of the movie. Total screening time was around 28 hours. The same steps were performed with another 3 participants (from Lebanon, Serbia and Italy), who watched Psycho, Bambi, Dancer in the Dark and Blue is the Warmest Color.

Figure 16. UI Main interface while watching the movie, UI Stats interface with real-time annotations and UI reset page

RESULTS

DOMINANT EMOTION HYPOTHESIS	TITLE	SEEN BEFORE?	SEEKING	PLAY	CARE	FEAR	GRIEF	RAGE	LUST	CLICK AGREE
			(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)	(e)	(f)	(g)	(h)
SEEKING	Psycho	no	0.81	-	-	0.18			0.01	0.68
SEEKING	Birds	yes	0.72	-	0.12	0.16	-	-	-	0.75
PLAY	Singin' in the Rain	yes	0.06	0.80	0.02	-	-	-	0.12	0.75
PLAY	Bambi	no	0.21	0.43	0.19	0.13	-	-	0.04	0.64
CARE	Pretty Woman	yes	0.50	0.26	0.16	0.01	-	0.03	0.04	0.69
CARE	I am Sam	no	0.14	0.14	0.53	0.03	0.12	0.03	-	0.52
FEAR	Night of the Living Dead	no	0.44	-	-	0.54	-	0.02	-	0.51
FEAR	Saw	no	0.58	-	0.04	0.38	-	-	-	0.58
GRIEF	Bitter Moon	no	0.72	0.08	0.09	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.08	0.59
GRIEF	Dancer in the Dark	yes	0.71	0.11	0.12	0.02	0.04	-	-	0.52
RAGE	Incident	yes	0.79	-	0.10	0.06	-	0.05	-	0.81
RAGE	Schindler's List	no	0.80	0.01	0.05	0.04	0.08	0.01	0.01	0.74
LUST	9 1/2 Weeks	yes	0.51	0.32	0.03	0.03	0.01	-	0.11	0.80
LUST	Blue is the Warmest Color	no	0.59	0.19	0.17	-	-	-	0.04	0.74

Table 2. Which emotions are clicked the most (a-g) by subject? Do clicked emotions fall onto equal emotion annotation by authors (h)?

Below is a representation of the movie watchers' clicks (colors) against our annotation (gray) agreement per movie (see Establishing the Ground Truth). The question was how far does the movie watcher agree with the authors?

In what we consider an overall observation of all movies which were self-annotated by our subject movie watchers, GRIEF, surprisingly, demonstrated significant decline and LUST does not exceed the PLAY emotion. In general, PLAY Unequivocal Movie Emotions and their scenes are usually depicted with dancing and music. CARE, on the other hand, is usually recognized by a dialogue between two persons. What we learn is that: When a movie is interesting it has lot of clicks and SEEKING. CARE is substitute for RAGE and GRIEF scenes. PLAY, CARE and FEAR when present, dominate SEEKING. Also, we believe that clicking on these emotions was, in some cases,

die to a neocortical processing e.g. subject had tears in their eyes in the closing scenes of Schindler's Lists; but they annotated SEEKING. Also, in very scary scenes as in The Night of the Living Dead, the clicking came a couple of seconds after the scream.

DISCUSSION

In this study, we focus on understanding the emotions of movie watchers. We endorse 7 Primary-process emotions depicted in Affective Neuroscience and use their definition of emotions. We endow a ground truth by analyzing 14 movies and assigning a single emotion per scene according to the emotion we believe we felt while watching a movie. We cre-

Figure 17 (a). Subject and authors' agreement for 12 MOVIES
 7 - SEEKING, 6 - PLAY, 5 - CARE, 4 - FEAR, 3 - GRIEF, 2 - RAGE, 1 - LUST
 gray color - authors, other colors - subject 1, black dots - subject 2
 height - intensity of clicks per scene

Figure 17 (b). Subject and authors' agreement for 12 MOVIES
 7 - SEEKING, 6 - PLAY, 5 - CARE, 4 - FEAR, 3 - GRIEF, 2 - RAGE, 1 - LUST
 gray color - authors, other colors - subject 1, black dots - subject 2
 height - intensity of clicks per scene

ate "Affective Timelines" for each movie, which we use as a benchmark in comparison with emotions annotated by the movie watcher. Further, a desktop and mobile application was designed, developed and provided to the movie watcher. Next, we explained to the movie watcher the main definition of 7 emotions and explained the usage of the application. We asked participants to annotate emotions by clicking on prevailing ones felt while watching the movie. Once a movie is finished, software provides statistics and movie watchers can observe their percentage of assigned emotion in the movie. After that, the movie watchers were asked to choose the main emotion that for them describes the movie. Participants provided the feedback to the research authors for further analysis and comparison. Our results found that an agreement varies between 0.51 - 0.81 among authors and movie watcher (see Table 2, "click agree" column). Obviously, our research has to consider several limitations:

Neuroscience measurements. It is worth mentioning that our model stands on Primary-process emotions which are presented by the research in Affective Neuroscience. We focus solely on 7 emotions (SEEKING, PLAY, CARE, LUST, FEAR, GRIEF and RAGE) as they are proven to exist in all mammals and were measured in exact brain areas and neurotransmitters. We are aware that we are not able to obtain exact fMRI scans and to verify the true measurements of participants' emotions during the movie watching. However, our future study will evolve physiological responses and measurements of movie watchers (heart rate, skin conductivity, etc.).

Specimen issue. Although 14 movies were used for data acquisition, the results of this study should be considered as preliminary as they do not contain a bountiful number of subjects (less than 10 movie watcher analyses per movie). However, we expect that a future analysis with a greater sample will demonstrate more significant results.

Multicultural difficulty of research. We should take into consideration that the research was conducted in multicultural setting as participants and authors were from 4 different European and Middle-Eastern countries. However, our hypothesis in research is that Primary-process emotions are same across all cultures (excluding the neo-cortex interpretations) and we believe that we are able to show the preliminary emotions with respect to the cultural origin. More subjects of diverse cultures are needed and will be the focus of future research.

Technological constraints. We should also take into account the designed and developed application. Namely, it could be supposed that there is a nuance in performance during the affect annotation. This hinders the synchronization of the movie and the movie watcher's affect timelines. We could therefore assume a tolerance of +/- 3%. In this research, we created an application and tried to use a natural surrounding for movie watching so that the watchers' level of immersion remains a priority.

Non-referenced attributes. Future study also involves the detailed analysis of perceptual elements (such as soundtrack,

color, shots, plot, etc.) that we believe are able to determine specific emotions in the watchers. We could classify movie genres according to these emotions and present emotional characteristics in percentages for each movie type: thrillers, cartoons for kids, love stories, and so on. Our ongoing study also involves the verification of the emotional "footprint" of famous directors, e.g. Hitchcock and his art of creating suspense (Truffaut, 1985).

Interpretations versus Primary-process emotions. In this research, we also used a categorical labeling of emotions, which might be a subject of neo-cortical interpretation. Although Ekman proposes Anger, while Panksepp proposes RAGE, we are still at the beginning when it comes to understanding Primary-process emotions. We believe that by setting up this benchmark (highest possible agreement among authors and movie watchers), it will provide us with insight into these emotions which will be compared against their physiological measurements. We are also aware that there are differences when focusing on two actors in the scene. One actor might be stimulating RAGE in the watcher, while the other may be inspiring CARE. We can conclude that more subjects are needed for more precise results.

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TOWARDS AN EMPIRICAL MODEL OF THE UX: A FACTOR ANALYSIS STUDY

Natalia Ariza, Jorge Maya
 Product Design Engineering Department; Universidad EAFIT, Colombia.
 ✉ narizav1@eafit.edu.co, jmayacas@eafit.edu.co

ABSTRACT

One of the key factors to bear in mind when it comes to developing innovative products is a satisfying and pleasurable user experience (UX). Although there are many models and definitions of UX, most of them have been proposed intuitively. From themes and elements previously identified as essential for an UX model, a study of exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was performed. We found eight factors in Before-UX-stage, 7 in During-UX and 17 in After-UX stage. Similar UX aspects are expressed in different ways through the different stages and factors. There are differences in terms of how a factor could weight and relate to others regarding the UX-stage. Moreover, while some factors are consistent with the literature, others are new. Most of the factors give us an idea about the articulation of variables and the way some factors relate to others.

KEYWORDS: *User experience-UX, UX-elements, UX-model, factor analysis, empirical research.*

INTRODUCTION

To develop innovative products, one of the key points is to strive for a satisfying and pleasurable user experience, UX, (Cagan, Vogel, 2002; Desmet, Hekkert, 2007). UX is a new paradigm to add value and differentiation, offering a broader perspective of the functionality and usability, focusing on how to create richer user experiences (Wimmer, 2011). The UX highlights the non-utilitarian aspects of interaction, focusing on the user's affection, perception and meaning and the value of such interactions. Currently, since in many product categories functionality and usability are highly satisfactory aspects, competition is focused on UX (Cagan, Vogel, 2002, Kano, 1987).

An UX literature review was conducted for 2003 – 2013 publications. Ariza, Maya (2014) identified UX models and definitions with some key dimensions: the subjective, context dependent and dynamic character of UX (Hassenzahl et al 2006, Law et al, 2009). Despite this, it was not possible to identify empirically constructed models based on observations that account for, as widely as possible, the complexity of the UX. These models and definitions are mainly based on authors' self-reflections or insights (Desmet 2003, Mahlke 2005, Roto 2006, Hassenzahl, 2003). According to (Hassenzahl, Tracktinsky, 2006), this lack of empirical research restricts a theoretical advance and limits the UX concept understanding and its future development. As UX gains importance in many design disciplines, it also becomes more important to define, de-

limit, categorize and theorize about it, in an attempt to make it more precise, comparable, and generalizable (Kaye, 2011).

Here, we assume UX as: “*The awareness of the psychological effects elicited by the interaction with the product*” p.5, (Hekkert, Schifferstein, 2008). This broad definition allows us to account for the complexity we want to capture in our analysis.

This work is part of a wider research of which the final objective is the development of a prescriptive product design method, with an emphasis on rich experiential products. This method would fill a lack of relatively accurate, simple and quick methods suitable for three scenarios. First, in generating structured and rich ideas about experiential products in the FFE (Fuzzy-Front-End). Second, work as a conceptual design method of experiential products in companies with short product development cycles, without specialized personnel, few financial resources and where the risk level is low (i.e., SMES with low-volume production and high rotation products). In other words, this method would allow for designing a product with very little users' field-research. Third, heuristically support the design process in companies that develop their products using conventional UCD tools.

The first step of this research was to identify and categorize the information about UX. This revealed many items with distinct categories, hierarchies, and limits, making the situation poorly controllable because of its complexity. The need to identify what elements would be essential in a UX model with the product was evident (Ariza, Maya 2014). In that paper,

13 UX models, 10 definitions and 10 UX review papers, were selected out of 387 publications, to support the theoretical framework for the research. We applied to this set of data, the thematic analysis technique, TA. TA allows for the identification and structural analysis of information patterns, especially of a psychological nature (Braun, Clarke, 2006). As a result, we identified the essential elements, (grouped into general themes and specific elements or variables and sub-variables), which should be in a UX model. The second step, which we report in this paper, would be how, based on these results from the TA, to design an experiment and then apply a data reduction technique (factor analysis) to identify correlations between variables and summarize groups of variable factors. This step will allow us to undertake a validation of the elements found in the TA and provide evidence of how they are connected, i.e. to which extent they match the structure of themes and elements. The third step of the project will be based on the results of that experiment, building a detailed, complete, concise and manageable UX model. The fourth step, based on the proposed UX model, would develop the prescriptive method sought.

In the TA, eight main themes with their essential variables (28) were identified (Table 1). Although it was possible to identify themes that had been referenced in other UX models, some variables or sub-variables within each theme were different to those in the literature, which showed that they were overlooked or linked to different variables.

Thematic Analysis Results

Table 1 outlines the definition of the themes and variables that an UX-model should include. They were used to construct the research instrument. The discussion of all the themes is detailed in (Ariza, Maya, 2014).

In section 2 and based on the TA results, we explain the experimental methodology used to find relationships between variables. In section 3, how the results were analyzed and interpreted and in section 4, we present the conclusions.

METHODOLOGY

First, the experiment scheme was designed. Second, a stimulus (product for the experiment) was defined. Third, the data collection instrument (questionnaire) was designed. Fourth, the sample and the experiment conditions were set-up.

Experiment General Scheme

Exploratory factor analysis, EFA, was chosen as the technique to identify correlations and factors grouping variables. These types of experiments should be conducted in a naturalistic context to consider the environmental and social effects, but without interferences due to excessive noise or intrusions. Moreover, it should consider the UX dynamics: before-during-after and long-term stages interaction. The experimental protocol was as follows: 1. Explain the experiment to the subject,

THEMES	VARIABLES
User	Physiological aspects
	Concerns (motives, interests, emotional sensitivities)
	Affective appraisal
Product	Instrumental property (functionality, usability)
	non-instrumental (aesthetic, emotional, semantic)
Interaction	Active, passive
	Instrumental aspect (usability)
	Non-instrumental (aesthetic, emotional, semantic)
Context and external factors	Context: physical, social and use (situation of use)
	External Factors: social, tech, cultural, economic
Consequences	Behavioral
	Multisensory
	Cognitive
	Affective
Purpose of use	Purpose of action
	Purpose of being
UX dynamics	Before, during, after, over time
Total UX	Experience and continuous feedback

Table 1. UX Model Themes and Elements
Source: Ariza, Maya (2014)

2. Generate expectations about the product selected through visuals and video information, 3. Apply UX-Before questionnaire, 4. First approach to the product, allowing interaction for 2 minutes, 5. Apply UX-During questionnaire, 6. Second approach, longer interaction (8 minutes), 7. Apply UX-After questionnaire, 8. Check responses. All the experiment was run in Spanish.

Product definition

We selected a product with features that would allow us to evaluate instrumental and non-instrumental aspects. Cameras, headphones, desktop mouse, watches, smartphones, were proposed. We ruled out those products where technological aspects had a lot of weight in the final UX or that were too simple. Finally, headphones were chosen because they are useful and with a relatively complex usability and UX. Then, we looked for headphones references which, apart from their functionality, were rich in their non-instrumental aspects (aesthetic, emotional, social, etc.).The Sony WALKMAN® and MP3 player 4GB with Speaker (Figure 1), 3 in 1, NWZ-WH303

Figure 1: Product used in the experiment. (Source: Ariza)

headphones were chosen. This product was new to the market at the time of the experiment, comprising expectation and novelty, aspects important to UX.

Design of the instrument

We began with the operationalization of the variables identified from the TA. We reduced ambiguity by using the definition themes and variables. Possible variables dimensions and sub-dimensions were identified. In most cases, it was necessary to observe more than one dimension to describe the variable, see an example in (Table 2). The questions were evaluated on a 5-point Likert scale (1-Strongly Disagree, 2-Disagree, 3-Neutral, 4-Agree, 5- disagree). To facilitate the handling of the data, each question was coded. For instance, for “Have I known what to do with the product”, the variable “product” with dimension “Instrumental” and sub-dimension “usability” was coded (PIU1). Some survey questions were specific to the product category, for example, “Music is important to me” or “It has good sound.”

To improve the reliability and content validity of the instrument, we took as reference questionnaires such as SUMI (Kirkowski, 1993), AttrakDiff (Perceived hedonic and pragmatic quality, Hassenzahl, 2003), UEQ (user experience Questionnaire, Laugwitz, 2008). This also allowed us to identify the type of questions used when looking to find information about usability, pragmatic, and hedonic UX aspects. Another important consideration was to find a way to consider the dynamic characteristic of the UX. A longitudinal approach was proposed, where with the same product, we would seek to gather opinions and feelings at different times. Before-UX (early or imagined experience), During-UX: momentary (experiencing), After-UX: episodic UX (reflecting on the experience), and finally, Over-time-UX: a long term-cumulative evaluation as a collection of multiple periods of interaction (not taken into account in this study due to time constraints).

We generated more than 230 questions in a first phase. A refinement of the questions was made comprising: 1.Reviewing the definitions of the concepts proposed with the final items to ensure good relationship and more clarity, 2.Two pilot tests conducted with 3 students to ensure a good understanding of the questions, and, 3. Reducing the questionnaire with the help of an expert. The final questionnaire had 153 questions composed as follows: Before-UX: 28 questions, During-UX with 37, After-UX with 88. Not all questions applied for every stage; for example “Does It feel good in the hands?” did not apply for the Before-UX stage. The final questionnaire was uploaded to Google Drive App. This questionnaire gave us the data required for the EFA. As an example, (Table 3) shows the coded questions for the Before-UX stage.

VARIABLE	DIMENSION AND SUB-DIMENSION	SUB-DIMENSION CONCEPTUAL DEFINITION	ITEMS-(QUESTION-CODES)-UX-STAGE
Product	Instrumental (Usability)	The extent to which a product can be used by specified users to achieve specified goals with effectiveness, efficiency, and satisfaction in a specified context of use, ISO 9241-11	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Did I know what to do with the product? (PIU1) DuringUX 2. Did I find the product safe to use? (PIU10) AfterUX 3. Are the headphones simple to use? (PIU11) DuringUX 4. Could I identify how to activate all their functions? (PIU12) AfterUX 5. Was it clear to use? (PIU2) AfterUX 6. It looks complex to use (PIU3) BeforeUX 7. Supplementary product information is useful (PIU4) AfterUX 8. Was it easy to learn to use? (PIU5) AfterUX 9. I was worried about damaging the product in the interaction (PIU6) AfterUX 10. Using the product was quick and agile (PIU9) AfterUX <p>Note: similar questions were asked in different UX stages</p>

Table 2. “Product” variable operationalization example
Source: Ariza, Maya (2014)

QUESTIONS	ITEMS	CODE
1	I would buy this type of product to listen to music	UX5
2	Music has always been an important part of me	FC1
3	I could use them anywhere	CXL5
4	I like to find different ways to listen to music	CM2
5	I like listening to music	Cl1
6	I like Electronic Products	Cl2

Table 3. Example Items for Before-UX stage
Source: Ariza, Maya (2014)

Sample selection

A sample for EFA should take into account the ratio of subjects-number of variables. We followed the indications of Nunnally (1978), Guilford (1954) and Kline (1986, 1994) on this, and (MacCallum et al,1999) for advice on commonality issues. We had 153 questions representing 28 variables. So, a possible sample of N=200 would be about 7 times the number of variables. Despite these precautions, we were aware that this sample size could bring restrictions when it came to generalizing results beyond the studied population.

A convenience sample was selected: Colombian EAFIT university students, 17 - 25 year-olds, from engineering, management and humanities. Students studying product design engineering and music were excluded to prevent the introduction of bias due to their training.

The resources used for the data collection were: 3 research assistants (bachelor students), 2 headphones in their original case, tablets to answer the questionnaire (in Spanish), a product's brand promotional video and a product leaflet.

RESULTS

Data collection took 15 days, from Monday to Friday in the mornings and evenings, within the University premises (coffee shops, squares, and meeting points) to preserve a natural UX setting and in off-peak hours to minimize intrusions.

Preliminary analysis

200 people were surveyed generating 200 valid surveys: 23,5% from administration, marketing and business students; 50,5% from engineering students (7 programs), and 26% from other courses (communication, law, economics, accounting, geology). Capturing subjects in different places and times generated a good representation.

Firstly, questionnaire data were explored using SPSS for before-during-after UX stages and for the Total-UX, indicating whether the questions were unambiguous. Communalities were >0.64, therefore the N=200 was adequate to continue with EFA on SPSS.

Data Optimization

Firstly, we ran the EFA for the entire set of variables (Total-UX), considering very low or very high correlations (Field, 2009). Consequently, 14 variables (below $.3 > r > .8$) were removed. Secondly, a KMO test=0,678 indicated to continue the EFA. (Field, 2009).

EFA was then ran a second time, with a Total-UX 139 variables. After eliminating low correlation variables, and before finding factors, KMO raised to 0.76. Similarly the KMO >0.5 was checked again allowing us to remove 15 more variables. The definitive EFA was then performed with 124 variables.

EXTRACTION AND ROTATION METHOD SETTINGS

Two extracting factor methods are recommended in EFA to generalize the results to larger populations: maximum-likelihood and Kaiser's alpha factoring (Field, 2009). Both methods were run, but results implied increasing the sample size or looking for an alternative factor extraction method. As the former option was not possible, we used Principal Component Analysis, PCA, with Oblimin rotation, bearing in mind that the PCA's conclusions are restricted to the "sample collected and generalization of the results can only be achieved if analysis using different samples". It generated two factor matrices: the pattern-matrix defining the factors, and containing the weights for calculating the factor scores and the structure-matrix, visualizing the relationships between factors.

Factor Extraction-Interpretation

We took variances above 0.40. Well-defined factors have at least three items with heavy weights (Field, 2009). A screeplot and the Kaiser criterion allowed us to retain all factors with eigenvalues >1, with an exception: for Before-UX stage EFA, that having less than 30 variables, eigenvalues >0.7 are recommended (Field, 2009).

Factors structure

EFA was performed to the variables of each UX stage: Before-During-After and Total UX, (Table 4). KMOs >0.5 and determinant close to 0 for all the UX-stages, showed the suitability of EFA. The Bartlett sphericity test $\text{sig} = .000 < .05$, indicated correlated variables. After rotation, the factors selected accounted for over 65% of all the variance. Cronbach's alpha coefficient, $\alpha = 0.92$ indicated good questionnaire reliability. Additionally, all factors had $\alpha > 0.80$.

The EFA statistical process won't be detailed. We focused on the interpretation and construct labeling of the factors. See (Tables 5-6-7). Some questions (variables) shown are the translation of the original textual form, but for space limitation, others appear as the key issue of the question. Moreover only the factor labeling and description of the Total UX are shown.

STAGE	ITEMS	DETERMINANT	SIG	FACTORS	EXPLAINED VARIANCE
Before-UX	19	0.000	0.000	8	75.4%
During-UX	33	2.454E-009	0.000	7	65,6%
After-UX	72	1.000E-013	0.000	17	69.2%

Table 4. EFA stages summary
Source: Ariza, Maya (2014), SPSS analysis

NUMBER	QUESTIONS	LOADING	FACTOR
1	I see myself using the product	,886	Anticipation to buy and use the product Factor. Reflects how the user envisages himself using and buying the product which motivates him to its use
	I'd buy this type of product to listen to music	,865	
	It triggers me to use them	,625	
2	I keep updated on technology issues	,893	Interest in the product's technology factor: Explains why the user is interested in technology and electronic products
	I like electronic products	,836	
3	It's a fashionable product	,792	Social approval factor: Represents the user's belief about the social acceptance of a fashionable product, linked to figuring out who would use the product
	I know what kind of people would use this type of product	,780	
4	I like listening to music	,902	Specific Concerns factor: Reflects the specific concerns attached to the activity performed with the product
	Music has always been an important part of my life	,867	
5	They look professional	,785	The professional look adaptability factor: Reflects how a product with a professional appearance could be used in any place
	I could use them anywhere	,706	
6	I'm feeling in a good mood today	,966	Mood factor: Reflects the user's current mood
7	The product looks valuable	-,850	The product value factor: Explains how given that the products is valuable for the user, she will be curious to find out more about it
	I am curious about the product	-,479	
8	The product looks attractive	-,793	Attractiveness-Interest Factor: Explains how an attractive product would be interesting and would entertain the user. Reflects the novelty value of the product as well.
	The product entertains me	-,620	
	I found the product interesting	-,608	
	It looks novel	-,550	

Table 5. Before-UX Factors
Source: Ariza, Maya (2014), Factor labeling and interpretation

NUMBER	QUESTION KEY	LOADING	FACTOR
1	Exciting interaction	,740	The High Stimulation Factor: Influences the user to have an stimulating and fascinating interaction with the product, based on its impressive appearance; consequently the person gets into the product
	Fascinating	,632	
	Astonishing	,627	
	Been engaged	,519	
2	Knowledge to do	-,837	Complete Usability Factor: Influences all the user's usability concerns: to know what the product is for, to understand the conceptual model proposed by the product, control, to know if the user needs more to learn to use it, if the product is easy to use, if it is challenging, if the controls provide clear information and if it has been easy to learn to use
	Easy to understand	-,822	
	Control	-,786	
	More Information	,768	
	Simple to use	-,722	
	Challenging	,685	
	Works logically	-,629	
	Clear Controls	-,629	
Easy to learn	-,583		
3	Previous Experience	,772	Previous experience Factor: Explains that if the user has already used the product category or is familiar with it, it allows the person to imagine different things to do with the product
	Familiarity	,651	
	Imagine other uses	,587	
4	Harmonic form	,808	Aesthetic sensations Factor: Influences aspects of visual, tactile and kinesthetic aesthetics.
	Feels good in hands	,804	
	Feels good using	,752	
	Comfortable	,721	
5	Boring	,698	The Boring product Factor: Causes the perception of the product as boring therefore diminishing the user's interest and connection with the product
	Interested (Willingness)	-,494	
	Connection	-,476	
6	Different purpose	,854	The Multi-Purpose product factor: Reflects that the product has multiple purposes, especially those linked to its main practical function (providing good sound) and an aesthetic-semantic property (the product's originality).
	Good sound	,485	
	Originality	,434	
7	Easy to remember features	,537	Cognitive Ergonomics Usability Factor: Concerns the comprehension of the product functionality, the easiness to recall the product characteristics, its affordability All these aspects are correlated to an appreciation of how well the product fits to its design purpose.
	Clear functionality	,537	
	Invite exploring	,523	
	Fulfills design purpose	,487	

Table 6. During UX-stage FA
Source: Ariza, Maya (2014), Factor labeling and interpretation

NUMBER	QUESTION KEY	LOADING	FACTOR
1	Interested (Decision)	,754	The product engagement Factor: After the interaction with the product the user wants to gather more knowledge about it. This information would allow the user to anticipate and imagine using the product in the future. This would eventually lead her to buy the product. Those aspects are also correlated to a confirmatory belief of "I've found the product I was looking for!"
	Want know more	,678	
	Research more	,677	
	Buy product	,665	
	Imaging using	,575	
	Keep exploring	,488	
	Looking for similar	,436	
2	Quick, agile	-,786	The learnability Factor: Is at the basis of a user's assessment of product use, linked to the amount of time required to understand the product functionality and the clarity of its use. Finally, is correlated to the user's ability to explain the product functionality to someone else.
	Hard to understand	,721	
	Clear to use	-,669	
	Could explain	-,435	
3	Expecting more	-,758	Full expectations Fulfillment Factor: Reflects largely whether the product fulfilled the user's expectations: whether it surpassed the user's expectations and whether the product fulfilled what it claimed it could do.
	Cover expectation	,653	
	Fulfilled expectation	,594	
	Functional	,404	
4	Evocation	,727	Reminiscing factor: Reflects the remembering effects on the user after the interaction, thus generating nostalgia and the loss of the track of time
	Nostalgic	,654	
	Lost track of time	,553	
5	Make original	-,587	Self-image fitness with social context factor: Determines the user's self-perception as an original person if he uses the product. This is linked to envisaging the use of a more common product as a way to make him feel more comfortable. These aspects are correlated to imagining himself looking good if he uses the product, envisaging the product as a fashionable item and using it in different activities.
	Prefer common	,567	
	Make look good	-,456	
	Fashionable accessory	-,453	
	Using different activities	-,405	
6	Explore new uses	,612	The explorative use factor: Is at the basis of exploring new ways to use the product. This exploration entails some anxiety while using the product and surprise with some product functions. These aspects are correlated with a change in the way the user listens to music linked to feeling competent to use the product.
	Anxiety	,531	
	Surprise	,517	
	Change how one listens to music	,437	
	Competence	,416	
7	Disconnect from world	,819	Absorption Factor: Causes the user to disconnect from the world, and concentrating while interacting with the product. Those aspects are correlated to a further repeated product use and to fit the user's lifestyle
	Liked listen music this way	,577	
	Focus when interacting	,551	
	Repeatedly use	,493	
	Fit lifestyle	,474	
8	Icons recognizable	,851	Indicative Functions clarity Factor: Implies easily recognizing the product's icons and symbols linked to indications about the product use from the product or from its user manual. It entails the ability to activate all the product's functions.
	Clear Indications	,808	
	Useful (leaflet)	,504	
	Identification of functions	,418	
9	Use according to place	,765	Contextual knowledge Factor: Is at the basis of knowing how to use the product according to different contexts and to the integration of other (electronic) products the user has.
	Integrate with other products	,650	

10	Uncertainty	-,633	The starting point Factor: Reflects the clarity of knowing how to identify an "entrance point" to start interacting with the product
11	Brand association	-,835	Brand Awareness Factor: Makes possible the linking of the product to a particular brand
12	Technological consistent	,788	Technology advances assessment Factor: Implies an assessment of the product's technological advances. This aspect is correlated with a judgment about the product as providing an innovative way to perform its main function (listening to music).
	Innovative	,606	
13	Enjoy using in place	,747	Physical Context Enjoyment Factor: Determines product enjoyment in a particular context. It is related to the product likeability for the user's friends.
	Friends would like product	,467	
14	Original use	,582	Novelty in use factor: Influences the appreciation of the novelty of using the product'. It's related to the user's aesthetic appreciation of the product.
	Liked the look	,510	
15	Familiar style	-,753	Product Category Style Factor: Defines that the user will look for a style similarity between the product and others regularly bought.
	Communicate personality	-,466	
16	Change perception	,805	Product Perception Shift factor: Influences a change in the user's product perception after using it
17	Need explanation	-,481	Additional Learning Resources factor: Causes the user to ask for additional explanations or time in order to be able to use the product.
	Need time to understand	-,464	

Table 7. After UX-stage FA
Source: Ariza, Maya (2014), Factor labeling and interpretation

RESULTS DISCUSSION

Although, we started with a preconceived idea of how the variables should group, the statistical results from the EFA showed that some emerged factors were in fact consistent with the literature, for instance, the Complete Usability Factor or the Aesthetic sensations-Factor. On the other hand, most of the remaining factors gave us insights about the articulation of variables within them, for instance, the Product-engagement Factor shows motivation related to a pleasing encounter with the product and an invitation to explore or buy it. And finally, other factors showed themes like the Reminiscing-factor that were overlooked or not that common in the literature but that may be important for the UX.

There are some factors, for example, determining UX's aesthetic aspects that are expressed in different ways and ranked in different importance positions through the different UX-stages: for the Before-UX stage aesthetics appear as an Attractiveness-interest factor, for the during-UX stage appears as a pure Aesthetic-Sensations factor, and for the after-UX stage appears split on two factors: *Novelty-in-use factor* and *Product-Category-Style* factor. To understand the results, each factor labeling was created to reflect the underlying influ-

ences causing the answers pattern, explaining why it involves particular variables, rather than just describe them.

Despite the EFA extraction method restriction and the heuristic labeling, we believe in the importance of an empirical approach and the potential of these factors and their correlations (that are not reported here due to space limitations) to challenge the UX understanding, in order to contribute to further developments.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper's originality lies in the empirical approach, supported by EFA, to model UX while using TA results (that involved very distinct UX aspects), as input for the experiment. We believe that the structure of the factors accounts for UX complexity because the whole EFA was the final result of the revision of many key topics found in UX modeling publications. EFA allowed us to identify the latent variables or factors, behind UX, whilst allowing to tackle and manage UX complexity. The correlations between factors will give us insights of the variable relationships in the UX model sought and the derived further product design method.

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NINE WAYS TO WAKE UP: BEDSIDE ALARM CLOCKS DESIGNED BY A 'MEANINGFUL INTERACTION' LEARNING APPROACH

Bahar Sener, Owain Pedgley
University of Liverpool, School of Engineering, UK
Middle East Technical University, Department of Industrial Design, Turkey
✉ bsener@metu.edu.tr, pedgley@metu.edu.tr

ABSTRACT

During interaction, people perceive and process varied sensorial information emanating from a product, leading to qualitatively varied experiences on aesthetic, meaning and emotional levels. Navigating a way through the complexity of issues involved in 'design for interaction' (Dfi) is however not easy. This paper presents the foundations and findings of an educational approach to designing for (or by) 'meaningful interaction', which we define as user-product interaction conceived through everyday adjectives and phrases. Product semantics and interaction semantics are compared and contrasted. A product design project (bedside alarm clock) is used as a vehicle for exploring meaning-based Dfi teaching and learning. Students responded well to the educational approach, delivering nine diverse, detailed, and convincing proposals for product interaction. The paper concludes on the 'role' of adjectives in Dfi and the need to synchronize product and interaction semantics to avoid experiential incongruities.

KEYWORDS: *design for interaction, generative design method, meaningful interaction, aesthetics of interaction, semantics*

INTRODUCTION

Industrial designers are not concerned with the specification and configuration of products in isolation, but with reference to people's relations and interactions with those products and for the wider events and experiences that result through product ownership and use (Moggridge, 2007; Suri, 2003; Stott, 2002; Forlizzi & Ford, 2000; Green & Jordan, 1999). User experience, as a combination of cognition, affect, behaviour and instinct (Crilly et al., 2008b; Hekkert & Schifferstein, 2008), is a subject that is intrinsic to designing for interaction. It is therefore not surprising that designing for user (or product) experiences has become a subject of considerable attention in design practice and design education in recent years.

In the context of physical artefacts, user-product interactions are fundamental to shaping people's experiences. The conceptualization of interactions at the front end of a project is a critical design step. However, 'design for interaction' (Dfi) is a multifaceted and complex activity, requiring understanding of various characteristics of products, users and usage. Its basic premise is to design a product such that it leaves a trail of positive impressions on people through a series of definable interaction 'events'.

Carefully thought-through interactions are seen as a powerful tool towards adding value to a product and positively influencing people's experiences of that product (Hekkert & Schifferstein, 2008). Let us take for example two competing smart phones: one Apple, one Samsung. As with many A-B product comparisons in the current era of high-quality consumer goods, the functionality of both the Apple and Samsung products are similar, their retail prices are comparable, their brands are arguably equally prestigious, their country of manufacture for the most part are likely to be the same, and both products are readily available in stores. Most of these factors are long established as central to people's evaluation of product quality and influential on purchasing decisions (Berkowitz, 1987; Dawar & Parker, 1994). However, faced with a situation of little variance amongst these factors, people must look to other factors – such as product styling, brand image and user-product interaction – to discern which product they prefer amongst many. This paper takes forward ideas for shaping the third of these factors.

Many different approaches may be taken to define the interaction experience offered by a product. These range from sensory-functional analyses (e.g. Locher et al., 2010) to affective analyses such as Kansei Engineering (Schütte et al., 2008;

Nagamachi, 1995). In this present paper, we focus specifically on an approach that may be termed ‘meaningful interaction’, which seeks to make use of meaning concepts (usually expressed as adjectives or phrases) to steer intended interaction experiences in a characterful direction. ‘Meaningful interaction’ is seen as an especially useful approach to Dfi because it can be used to shape the qualitative experience of user-product interaction in a direct and comprehensible manner, by making reference to everyday lexicon and language.

FROM EXPERIENCE OF FORM TO EXPERIENCE OF INTERACTION

The principle that designers add value to products by carefully crafting ‘meanings’ into those products and their related ecology is well known and well studied. Product meanings may be present at a macro-scale, for example simply the presence or absence of a product in a particular environment or at a particular occasion can be the source of meaning. The provenance of a product can also be a deep source of meaning. Closer to the micro-scale, the choice and arrangement of product forms are complex provocateurs of meaning (Krippendorff & Butter, 1984).

Vihma (1995) stressed that whilst product form is inevitably a physical phenomenon, it is crucially an integral part of the perception process between people and products. Norman (1986) adapted visual communication models to the realm of everyday physical products and championed the terms ‘conceptual model’ (of the designer), ‘mental model’ (of the user) and ‘system image’ (of the product), as the three participants involved in ‘expressing’ and ‘discerning’ product functionality. Accordingly, we may say that product form can be ‘read’ to identify visual cues about both the functioning of a product (how we ‘use it’ – e.g. affordances, constraints, mappings, conventions etc.) and its standalone expressive characteristics (what kind of ‘personality’ it possesses – e.g. workmanlike, flamboyant, reliable, premium etc.). It is well known that visual qualities are an important factor in users’ initial evaluations of a product (Hsiao & Chen, 2006; Creusen & Schoormans, 2005; Bloch, 1995). Nelson (1970) alluded to this in his definition of ‘search attributes’ of a product, which may also be described as “... any informational stimuli that can be ascertained through the senses prior to consumption and, according to the consumer, have predictive validity for the product’s quality performance upon consumption” (Steenkamp & Trijp, 1996; p.97). These matters combine into the specialist field of design referred to as ‘product semantics’, concerned with conveying what a product ‘is’, ‘does’ and ‘means’ through product form (Demirbilek & Sener, 2003).

Product semantics represent a visual and static perspective on the role of a product to conjure meaningful experiences and to convey intended messages. This is a statement of fact rather than an accusation, since vision is the dominant sense during product appraisals (Lee et al., 2002). But what happens if we look beyond the visual and the static, towards the multimodal and the dynamic? The answer is that we come across

the concept of ‘meaningful interaction’, where multiple senses might be activated during people’s to-ing and fro-ing between a product during operation. In this process, experience of form gives way to experience of instrumental¹ user-product interaction. Let us explain a little more about how we define meaningful interaction, via the relatively newly coined phrase ‘aesthetics of interaction’ (Hummels & Overbeeke, 2010; Locher et al., 2010).

Aesthetics of Interaction

The definition of ‘aesthetic’ (*adj.*) provided by The Cambridge Dictionaries Online (2011) is “relating to the enjoyment or study of beauty” and as a term has traditionally been associated in industrial design with product appearance or styling (Holins & Pugh, 1990). This, in turn, has linked aesthetics to the professional design subjects of form, surfaces, materials and finishes influencing product visual properties. But in its contemporary setting, the term ‘aesthetics’ is used to cover multiple senses. For example, the *purring sound of a dishwasher* or the *squashable grip of a toothbrush* are as much aesthetic experiences as the *shimmering finish on a digital camera* or the *sleek lines of a motorcar*. During interaction with a product, we may gain pleasure or displeasure from whichever of our six senses (visual, tactile, kinesthetic, auditory, olfactory, gustatory) are activated at any given time. Designers who seek to define such aesthetic experiences are said to be concerned with *how* an interaction is experienced, or with the *aesthetics of interaction*. They may be concerned with, for example, the *smoothness* of a gear change on a sports car, the *sharpness* of kitchen knife as it effortlessly slices through a fruit, the *comforting softness* of a lounge sofa, or the *slickness of navigation* around a touchscreen operating system. ‘Aesthetics of interaction’ plays to our hedonic needs (Hassenzahl, 2003), since in its absence, a product may still provide acceptable functionality albeit with less panache.

Meaningful Interaction

Meaningful interaction is a concept that combines the principles of both aesthetics of interaction and product communication theory into an actionable approach to Dfi. It seeks to merge the following into a coherent interaction vision.

- Product communication theory: proposing designs for which people will be persuaded to interact with a product in a particular way to achieve a certain task, and be blocked from interactions that are considered detrimental (Crilly et al., 2008a; Greenberg, 2008). Krippendorff (2006) provides the invaluable insight that: “... one always acts according to the meaning of whatever one faces...”.
- Aesthetics of interaction: proposing designs for which the quality of the realized product interaction is appreciated, found pleasurable, irresistible, etc.

1 An instrumental interaction is one where a person is using/operating (or trying to operate) the product. A non-instrumental interaction is performed casually or with intent to explore or fact-find rather than operate – see Demir (2008).

In Desmet & Hekkert's affective framework of product experience (2007), a triad of interrelated sub-experiences (comprising aesthetics, meanings and emotions) is used as an additive approach to defining overall experiences from user-product interactions. What we mean by this is that a progression through the sub-experiences is defined, principally in an iterative manner, involving ever increasing distance away from phenomena of products (e.g. sensorial information emanating from a product, aesthetic experience) towards phenomena of people (e.g. core affect, emotive experience). With this perspective, 'meaningful interaction' essentially becomes the semantics of user-product interaction, or interaction semantics – where the subject of study is the meaning people attach to sensorial information experienced during interaction. In other words, we can say that sensorial information (from an interaction) 'speaks to us' (semiotics, signs) and that we can 'tell something' from it (semantics, meanings).

METHODOLOGY

As alluded to earlier, designers are familiar with using adjectives or phrases to guide form creation in a particular direction, with a view to conveying intended messages through product form and expressive visual characteristics. The central 'problem' in the work reported through this paper was to take the same thinking behind adjectival design approaches to form creation and apply it to meaningful interaction experiences that we may have with new products. That is, how to develop and apply an educational approach that focused not on, for example, generating an adventurous [looking] product but instead generating an adventurous interaction experience with a product? What kind of teaching and learning steps might be required? To do this, a seven-week research and design project was initiated as part of the elective course 'Design for Interaction' given to graduate industrial design students enrolled at the Department of Industrial Design, Middle East Technical University.

Design for Interaction – A Teaching & Learning Framework

The purpose of the 'Design for Interaction' course is to provide students with an introduction to interaction design (IxD) and user experience design (UXD) within the specific context of materialized products. It therefore serves as a bridge between students' skills gained through undergraduate industrial design training and more advanced studies in the fields of product experience. Although the course is necessarily quite broad in its subject matter, a key principle is always that students must apply what they have learned through a relatively long (up to half a semester) major project. Our teaching and learning is tied to a framework of five elements that have been refined over a six-year period. We have found that these elements adequately equip students for macro-level and micro-level ideation and development of interaction experiences for new products.

1. Domains of interaction: The various arrangements in which products can be connected to people.
2. Design communication theory: How people understand the usage of products from the information that products convey.
3. Contexts: Factors outside the control of the designer, which influence and condition the actors and situation in which an interaction takes place and within which design creativity can manifest.
4. User experiences: The various levels at which people can be affected by user-product interactions.
5. Technologies: New and emerging technologies that improve the interactivity of products or offer novel ways for interaction and connectivity to other products.

Design Project – Bedside Alarm Clock

Students used their course learnings to work on meaningful interactions for new bedside alarm clock concepts. This product was chosen because of its good potential for multimodal interaction, its relative simplicity in functionality and because its form need not be constrained by conventions. During the project, students defined an interaction vision, and then realized that vision through individual interaction episodes encountered along the path of interaction. To help navigate the possibilities of multimodal interaction, and to act as a source of idea inspiration, we constructed and made available to students a taxonomy of sensorial information (Figure 1) from an associated literature review. The taxonomy was inspired in part by the Kansei approach to product evaluation (Satterfield, 2003), in which a product is regarded as a transmitter of sensorial information across sensory modalities.

The project was managed through six stages, which in combination defined a method for ideation of meaningful interactions. Each stage is now described in detail.

Stage 1 – 'Visualized Connotations'. Each student was assigned an adjective, which would later form the basis of a product interaction proposal (adaptive, amusing, calm, charming, cheerful, engaging, helpful, innovative, simple). The adjectives were chosen by the course tutors so as to stimulate a wide variety of different interaction approaches and positive user experiences. Adjectives with negative connotations were not used. Krippendorff (2006) insists that without such adjective or associative constructions, it would be difficult for people (in our case, designers) to distinguish the properties of things (yet to be realized). Students made a semantic exploration of their assigned adjective and prepared seven A3 posters, as follows.

- i) By using <www.thesaurus.com> students decided on the particular 'sense' in which they would explore their adjective, and noted down given synonyms for that sense (Figure 2.a).
- ii) By using <www.dictionary.com> students chose a definition of their adjective and two preferred synonyms, which when

combined would verbally communicate the essence of the connotations that the student sought to evoke (Figure 2.b).

- iii) Students collated high-quality images of products (Figure 2.c-d) and non-products (Figure 2.e-f) that they considered to strongly embody their adjective and synonyms.
- iv) From their 'product' images, students identified and justified which kinds of sensorial information they considered to convey their adjective and synonyms (Figure 2.g).

Stage 2 – ‘Design Brief’. Students were made aware that the semantic explorations of the preceding stage would be taken forward in the context of meaningful interaction. The full design brief was distributed, explaining that the assigned adjectives would form the basis of product and interaction ideation and development. Students were free to determine the target user for their product, based on an understanding of who may value an ‘...adjective...’ interaction.

Stage 3 – ‘Acting-Out Interactions’. This stage asked students to think deeply about their adjectives and synonyms and to work towards an interaction vision by building relevant usage scenarios and considering how an ‘...adjective...’ interaction might be experienced. Students physically acted-out their interaction and storyline ideas using supplied primitive forms (Figure 3).

Stage 4 – ‘Product Critique’. As an in-class exercise, students were divided into groups to source Internet images and videos for ‘bedside alarm clocks’. Each group created a map of product attributes that they found worthwhile for discussion, including features, interaction, forms, and technology.

Stage 5 – ‘Product Development and 1-to-1 Critiques’. Students continued to develop their ideas by creating a storyboard (visual narrative) of potential interactions and product attributes. At this point, they were reminded to consider how each of the five course elements would influence their designs, but to work holistically on the product.

Stage 6 – ‘Final Presentation’. The completed projects were submitted as (i) a presentation board (Figure 4.a), (ii) a fact sheet, (iii) a lo-fi physical mock-up for live acting-out of interactions, (iv) augmented reality content that projected multimodal information onto presentation boards and mock-ups, bringing static visuals/objects ‘to life’ (Figure 4.b).

Figure 4.a-b. ‘Poly’ bedside alarm clock with CHARMING interaction: example presentation board and augmented reality mock-up (by Ahmet Burak Aktaş).

Figure 3. Acting-out possible interaction and storyline ideas using supplied primitive forms (by Ahmet Burak Aktaş).

ANALYSIS OF MEANINGFUL INTERACTION PROPOSALS

Figure 5 illustrates the nine bedside alarm clock proposals, which are now described in detail.

‘Adaptive Interaction’ in the sense of serving or able to adapt; showing or contributing to adaptation. Chosen synonyms: ‘flexible’ (elastic, stretchy, malleable) and ‘adjustable’ (modifiable, tailor-made, made to fit). ‘Mr.Quiet’ is a mechanical product ‘creature’ adaptive to users’ sleep location and posture. Each day the user must set the alarm based on the amount of sleep he or she wants to have, by pulling and extending the creature’s tongue. Printed on the tongue is a scale of hours/minutes and a comment on whether the sleep duration is sufficient or not. The product is clipped to a nearby object (e.g. pillow, pyjama) and quietly makes its way back to the clip as the hours of sleep pass. It operates discretely by sounding its alarm and vibration in close proximity to the person sleeping.

‘Amusing Interaction’ in the sense of pleasantly entertaining or diverting. Chosen synonyms: ‘gratifying’ (tending to gratify; giving or causing satisfaction; pleasing) and ‘witty’ (possessing wit in speech or writing; amusingly clever in perception and expression: a witty writer). The operation of ‘Monolight’ uses magnetic resistance embedded in various locations around the anonymous looking cuboid body. The user sets the alarm time with a special magnetic stylus: as the magnetic resistance is felt more strongly, so the speed of the alarm adjustment increases. This gives a precision kinesthetic feel to the interaction, as well as a sense of amusement through its novelty. The amusement continues at alarm time, when a purring cat is sounded, gradually morphing into a wild cat if the alarm is not cancelled. To cancel the alarm, ‘Monolight’ must be turned on its head and into a recess, which requires effort to act against magnetic repulsion – surely waking up the user in the process.

‘Calm Interaction’ in the sense of peaceful, quiet. Chosen synonyms: ‘harmonious’ (forming a pleasingly consistent whole, congruous) and ‘smooth’ (free from projections or unevenness of surface; not rough). ‘Zen’ harnesses elements of nature for its interaction, and through each element a sense of calm is conveyed. The product gradually illuminates (mimicking sunrise) and emits initially quiet but increasingly loud sounds as the alarm time approaches, to get the body prepared peacefully for waking up. Users define a soundscape by layering different ‘nature’ sounds (e.g. leaves, campfire, thunder) to wake up to. Each sound is represented tangibly as a pebble, making the placing and replacing of pebbles a ritualistic approach to alarm setting and cancelling.

‘Charming Interaction’ in the sense of pleasing; delightful: a charming child. Chosen synonyms: ‘elegant’ (graceful in form or movement: an elegant wave of the hand) and ‘fascinating’ (of great interest or attraction; enchanting; charming; captivating: a fascinating story). The icosahedron product form of ‘Poly’ is purposefully captivating to generate curiosity and desire to pick it up and handle it. The product takes on the responsibility not only to tell the user when to wake up but

also when to go to bed (if desired) in an elegant, carefully composed manner. It has unobtrusive and clear functions shared with a smart phone (app) interface. In the morning, a random face of the icosahedron lights up, asking the user to pay special attention to locating it and shutting off the alarm by placing the illuminated face downward.

‘Cheerful Interaction’ in the sense of promoting or inducing cheer, pleasantness, brightness. Chosen synonyms: ‘joyful’ (causing or bringing joy, as an event, a sight, or news; delightful) and ‘happy’ (delighted, pleased, or glad, as over a particular thing). ‘Daisy’ is animated, colorful and playful. It brings brightness at the time of waking up. The head of the clock – containing a light and ringer – leans over as it counts down to the alarm time, getting ever closer to the sleeping person’s head and readying them for waking up. Unusually, one interacts directly with the ‘clock hands’ to set the alarm time; once the alarm time is reached, the mechanical hands literally ‘clap’ to sound the alarm.

‘Engaging Interaction’ in the sense of winning; attractive; pleasing. Chosen synonyms: ‘attractive’ (arousing interest or engaging one’s thought, consideration) and ‘inviting’ (attractive, alluring, or tempting). ‘DingDong’ tries to make the waking up process more engaging through a multi-sensory experience. Two minutes ahead of the alarm time, the product starts to warn the user with increasing auditory and visual alerts. When it is time to wake up, the display physically pops out and exposes the loudspeaker, resulting in an unsilenced and louder alarm tone. The display also exhibits a swinging motion to alert the user. Making an effort to place the display back on its base cancels the alarm.

‘Helpful Interaction’ in the sense of giving or rendering aid or assistance like a caring, human-oriented and humanlike friend. Chosen synonyms: ‘friendly’ (characteristic of or befitting a friend; showing friendship) and ‘humane’ (tenderness, compassion, and sympathy for people and animals, especially for the suffering or distressed). ‘IntelliWake’ is helpful in that it provides humanlike advice and greetings on its display, along with feedback about sufficiency of sleep durations based on the planned alarm time. Throughout the sleeping hours, the product displays how much sleep time is left. With the accompanying app, users can track their sleep durations over time and use the information to change sleeping habits for the better.

‘Innovative Interaction’ in the sense of using or showing new methods, ideas; tending to introduce something new for the first time. Chosen synonyms: ‘creative’ (characterized by originality of thought; having or showing imagination) and ‘new’ (fresh and unused, up-to-date, novel). Innovative interaction is provided in ‘GameClock’ through gamification of the waking up process and the form and functions provided on the product. The product is used as part of a social network, offering ‘points’ to members based on whether they can wake up early compared to their friends. Points are deducted for snoozing and delaying the getting-up process. Points turn to real rewards once a total has been reached, depending on the interests of the social network.

'Simple Interaction' in the sense of clear, easy to understand, deal with, use, etc. Chosen synonyms: 'quiet' (not showy or obtrusive, subdued) and 'self-explanatory' (explaining itself, needing no explanation, obvious). In 'Sooth Up', dual functionality of a bedside lamp and alarm clock is provided. The product body is used as a tangible joystick controller offering simple movements: the x-axis mapped to alarm time up/down, and the y-axis mapped to lamp intensity up/down. To simulate the dawn, the product gently glows and its alarm becomes audibly louder as the alarm time approaches. Snoozing or cancelling is mapped to pushing the product body forwards or backwards.

DISCUSSION & CONCLUSIONS

The portfolio of product designs demonstrated very successfully to students how changes in the qualities of multimodal interaction dramatically affect user experiences. Furthermore, the variety in visual attributes of the proposals illustrates how changes in interaction vision can help steer product designs away from convention to potentially fruitful commercial ground. Students commented that the 'element-based' approach to learning interaction theory and terminology prepared them well for the design project. We would like to share our main observations regarding the process and possible improvements to designing for meaningful interaction.

In retrospect, it seems necessary to clarify the role of the adjective. All adjectives were used as a common tool to help

achieve positive user experiences from interesting new products. The design task was to 'use' the adjective (generatively, by designers) and not to explicitly 'convey' the adjective (evaluatively, to users). Seen this way, we did not expect product proposals to unequivocally communicate the adjective. It would be acceptable for users to detect the essence of the adjective or its synonyms, with the more important effect of being left with a positive product impression from the interaction. In this regard, the educational approach we took is best described as 'design by' rather than 'design for' meaningful interaction, in the sense that the adjectives were principally used as a design tool for students to be inspired and guided in their ideation.

The location of the interaction experience was another issue raised during the work. In the portfolio of designs, we see that where adjectival emphasis is placed can change. For example, a variation in meaningful interaction occurred during product set-up, operation, set-down, and storage/standby. We saw adjectives (i) driving overall product/interaction appraisals (e.g. the product *is cheerful*), (ii) shaping overall user affect/experience (e.g. the product *makes me cheerful*), (iii) shaping affect/experience when being woken (e.g. the product *wakes me up cheerfully*), and (iv) influencing product/interaction appraisals when the alarm sounds (e.g. the product *is cheerful when when the alarm goes off*). It is worth noting that a bedside alarm clock is a 'set and wait' type of product with long periods of inactivity, in contrast to an 'interactive' product such as a food mixer, hairdryer or smart phone – where meaningful interaction may manifest more obviously and frequently.

Figure 5. [From left to right, top to bottom] Completed bedside alarm clocks with 'adaptive', 'amusing', 'calm', 'charming', 'cheerful', 'engaging', 'helpful', 'innovative', and 'simple' interaction.

Regarding crossovers between product semantics and interaction semantics, students were specifically asked to design for interaction, but of course not without a degree of attention to product form and styling. Inevitably the choice and design of product elements for user-product interaction affects the overall form and stylistic direction of product proposals (and vice versa). For future work, we conclude that it would be worth considering how to integrate 'product semantics' and 'interaction semantics' into a unified method. This would require special attention to experiential incongruities that may arise from misaligned styling and interaction visions.

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HUGBUG

A WEARABLE INTERFACE FOR FACILITATING DIGITAL DESIGN FOR CHILDREN

Foad Hamidi

Lassonde School of Engineering, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, York University, Toronto

✉ fhamidi@cse.yorku.ca

Natalie Comeau

University Health Network, Toronto

✉ Natalie.comeau@gmail.com

Karla Saenz

Department of Design, Science, Arte, and Technology, Universidad Iberoamericana, Mexico City

✉ karla.saenz@uia.mx

Melanie Baljko

Lassonde School of Engineering, Department of Computer Science and Engineering, York University, Toronto

✉ mb@cse.yorku.ca

ABSTRACT

Wearable interfaces allow computational components to be woven into fabric. The potential of wearable interfaces to stimulate design thinking in diverse populations has been explored in recent years. Our development, which we have called the HugBug is a fun wearable interface in the shape of a hat supplemented with programmable LED lights and a touch sensor used as an example to demonstrate an Input-Process-Output model to children and stimulate design thinking. The interface was used in two workshops in Canada and Mexico.

KEYWORDS: *Wearable computing; tangible design; Children; digital media; intercultural collaboration.*

INTRODUCTION

Novel computational components allow for the incorporation of diverse materials, from paper and clothing (Qiu et al., 2013) to anything that is conductive (e.g., fruit or water), into digital user interfaces. The educational and inspirational potential of these approaches provide fertile ground for exploration. We are pleased to present the HugBug, a wearable interface used as a teaching tool. We used HugBug to introduce digital design to children and youths and to illustrate the application of a simple Input-Process-Output (IPO) model (IBM Corporation, 1974) to inspire physical computing interface design.

HugBug is meant to elevate the experience of hugging by adding light and sound. It consists in a large hat supplemented with a programmable bright RGB LED strip and a glove with touch sensors (Figure 1). Technically, when the wearer hugs someone, the touch sensors send a signal to the microcontroller that triggers a light show on the hat and gradually increases the volume of the music played. When the hugging stops, so does the light show and the volume of the music begins to decrease. The LED strip is controlled by a Flora microcontroller that uses it to start a light show when touch is detected by the sensor. A backpack contains a source of music (e.g., laptop and speakers) that is activated in time with the light show.

HugBug was originally developed as a fun interface to engage people in emotionally expressive behavior (e.g., hugging) in public spaces. It adds digital media to the already performative act of hugging, making it potentially more appealing. The design was inspired by the observation that there is a lack of physical contact between people in public urban environments, which can contribute to a sense of isolation and alienation. Similar to public performance acts such as Improv Everywhere (<http://improveverywhere.com>) and theatre and technological social probes such as the coMotion (Kinch et al., 2014) project, HugBug, as a fun interactive piece, aims to raise awareness of this issue and to promote communication in public spaces. HugBug encourages friends and strangers to initiate physical contact and thus promotes expression, performance and a stronger sense of community.

We first demoed HugBug at the Toronto Mini Maker Faire, a social event for makers, technology enthusiasts and amateur inventors (Figure 1). The invention was well received with over 30 people (both adults and children) hugging the second author who wore the hug-enhancing device. We made several observations during the demo: initially most people found the HugBug interesting but were reluctant to engage with it through hugging. Because of its public and physical nature, hugging between strangers usually requires verbal or non-

Figure 1. HugBug showcased at the Toronto Mini Maker Faire

verbal (e.g., inviting gesture) permission before initiation. Once permission was given, about one third of the people encountered engaged in hugging. The rest preferred to observe the hug and accompanying lights and music. Those who did take part in the hugging enjoyed the experience and many encouraged their friends to try it. Because of the position of the lights (i.e., on top of the hat), they were perceived more by the audience than the huggers. In contrast, because of the location of the speakers, the huggers, rather than the audience, heard the music. Most hugs lasted from 3 to 8 seconds, which was shorter than expected. In future, we plan to perform more public space experiments with the HugBug to explore the effect of the social and cultural context in which it is used and the effect produced by the person wearing the device.

USING HUGBUG TO FACILITATE DESIGN THINKING

HugBug can be thought of as an interface that turns its wearer into a cyborg, in the sense of a human augmented with digital technology (Gray et al., 1995). In this way, it can offer a good illustration of how we can extend human capabilities and expressive power with technology. In our labs in Toronto, we have been using a simple Input-Process-Output (IPO) model to teach digital design to youths and children in workshops (Figure 2). IPO and similar models were developed in the 1970s by the computer industry to capture and express software and hardware design (IBM Corporation, 1974). To have concrete and tangible examples is important for conveying abstract ideas, especially for children and youths, which is why we decided to use the HugBug as an example illustrating the use of the IPO model in concrete terms. We used the device in two physical computing and digital design workshops: one in Canada and one in Mexico.

The Canadian workshop was organized as part of a one-day event for 100 high school students (grades 9 and 10) who attended with their teachers (82 boys, 18 girls). We used the HugBug as part of a presentation to introduce the students to digital design (See Figure 3). The workshop was intended as a general overview of emerging technologies and included a discussion of rapid prototyping methods and open-source hardware, as well as, wearable computing. After introducing the IPO model, we showed a short video of how HugBug worked and described its design and underlying technology to the students. During informal interviews after the workshops with students and their teachers, they expressed that both IPO and HugBug were intuitive and inspiring. They were intrigued with the possibility that they could also design and implement their own wearable interfaces and use lights in their clothing. Despite the good feedback, HugBug was used as just one example in this workshop and it was hard to assess its usefulness.

In the second workshop, in Mexico, we worked with a group of 25 children between the ages of 3 and 15 (10 girls, 15 boys). The aim of the workshop was to introduce the children to digital design, to enable them to incorporate digital components into their own designs (Hamidi et al., 2014). We introduced the children to the IPO model and used HugBug as an example of how technology can be used to expand human expression. While we showed several examples of fun tangible

Figure 2. The simplified IPO model

Figure 3. HugBug described in a workshop for high school students

Figure 4. In a workshop for children, participants drew their designs on paper and added glitter and LED lights.

designs, we focused on HugBug, describing its design and implementation. When we were using it to demonstrate the IPO model, a couple of the children made the observation that if (as we suggested) sensors could be thought of as technological equivalents of human senses and microcontrollers as the human brain, then, wires would be equivalent to nerves in the body. This observation shows a deep understanding of the model. The children then tried on the interface, asked numerous questions and cracked jokes (mainly about the size of the hat). This generated a generally happy mood, which we believe is conducive to creativity and learning. As designers, it was important that we were present and could answer questions directly. This interaction made digital design seem more accessible and within reach.

After seeing the examples, the children drew Mexican folk art creatures, first indicating where touch sensors and lights would be and then embedding them there. The main idea was to extend the creatures' sensory powers by planting touch sensors on their bodies and extending their expressive powers through electric lights. The outcome of the workshop was more than 30 drawings, 18 of which were of detailed creatures that were enhanced with blinking LED lights and touch sensitive batteries (e.g., see Figure 4). The rest of the drawings were of things other than creatures or were unfinished. The children were proud of their work and showed them to the adults in the center and to each other. Through their drawings, the children showed a useful understanding of the IPO model and an ability to apply it to new contexts (Hamidi et al., 2014).

RELATED WORK: WEARABLES AND LEARNING

The potential of wearable computing (and more generally, *computational textile or e-textile*) as a teaching tool that can reach a diverse population of users is explored by many research projects such as the LilyPad ProtoSnap (Qiu et al., 2013) and EduWear (Katterfeldt et al. 2009), kits specifically developed for education. Qiu et al. have proposed the design of a computer science education curriculum using computa-

tional textile and wearable interfaces (Qiu et al., 2013). The researchers suggest that computational textiles allow for the engagement of diverse users, including users more interested in design and aesthetics rather than implementation and coding, with computational concepts and methodologies. Additionally, Katterfeldt et al. (2009) argue that the “soft”, not initially technical-looking character” of fabric as a material is more inviting to diverse groups of children and allows for novel artistic expression. In our approach, the focus is not on wearables as an implementation platform but as tools for inspiration that can facilitate different forms of digital design.

Katterfeldt et al. identify the potential of computational textiles for implementing personally meaningful and relevant designs (2009). According to constructionism (Papert, 1980), an influential development theory, this characteristic is a prerequisite for deep engagement in the activity of meaning construction that, in turn, facilitates learning and empowerment. Historically, we have a long and intimate relationship with our clothing. Clothing textiles and cloth are among humanity's earliest and most effective technologies that, according to Marshall McLuhan, “extend” our ability to adapt to different environments (McLuhan, 1994).

Another aspect of wearables is that through connecting to our physical body directly, they can sense our internal physical characteristics and externalize them. This characteristic is used to teach physical education through sensing and communicating characteristics such as heartbeat, speed (Dittert & Schelhowe, 2010), anatomy and physiology through externalizing internal body organ representations and processes (Norooz and Froehlich, 2013). Several previous projects have explored hugging as a mode of interaction. Huggy Pajama (Teh et al., 2008) is a wearable interface that allows parents to hug their children remotely, and the Huggable (Stiehl et al., 2006) is a robotic companion that has “sensitive skin” and can be interacted with through touch and hugging. The HugBug is different from these systems in that it does not simulate or replicate human hugs but rather enhances and promotes them.

CONCLUSION

We have introduced HugBug, a fun wearable interface, to enhance and promote hugging. We used it to illustrate the application of an Input-Process-Output model in two workshops for youths and children. We found the model useful in inspiring design thinking and illustrating the model.

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THE INFLUENCE OF AESTHETICS ON YOUNG PEOPLE'S TRUST OF INFORMATION

Allison Sivak

✉ allison.sivak@ualberta.co

ABSTRACT

We live in a time and place that has been termed “the new age of aesthetics,” in which “design is everywhere, and everywhere is now designed” (Postrel 2003). “Everywhere” could refer to our physical environments as well as to our cultural and informational environments; we find information framed by or contained in various “objects,” which may be print, digital, or multi-media; small- or large-scale; discrete “containers” or immersive environments. I am interested in the ways in which the design of information materials works to communicate with young readers, and how young people interpret the visual and other aesthetics of those materials, as well as how they interpret the text. I am researching the ways in which young people assign credibility to information materials as potentially distinct from the ways in which adults working in the design professions would assign credibility to those same materials. This paper focuses on a research project in progress, regarding information design. The research project takes up to five information materials on the subject of the environment, aimed towards young readers. I will ask up to five designers and up to eight pairs of young people (aged 11-17) to review the information material. I will then compare where their interpretations converge and where they diverge.

KEYWORDS: *information design, adolescents, information literacy, aesthetics, qualitative methods*

INTRODUCTION

This research will examine some affordances and interpretations of information design for young people, based on interview sessions with pairs of young people and individual designers. Taking a selection of five differently designed information materials on the subject of the environment, I examine how two distinct groups interpret those materials: adult designers and young people between the ages of 11-17. I will document participants' discussions about the aesthetic properties of specific information materials. My analysis of their discussions will look to identify how design elements influence (or do not influence) participants' attention to the materials, and to examine some of the ways in which young people talk about design aesthetics. I am particularly interested in how the discussions and terminology used by young research participants regarding the aesthetics of information design may converge or contrast with discussions and terminology provided by the discussions and terminology provided by designers. I am in the early stages of this research, which will be completed by August 2014.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The term “information” is often used in a deceptively neutral way, suggesting that information exists free of influence or affect. Prasad (2005) notes that the writing, design, and reception of an informational text possess an inherent complexity, regardless of what appears to be on the surface, simple. Lanham (2006), a composition scholar, went further when he noted, “clean information is not the destiny of humankind. Clean information is unnatural and unuseful. Information always comes charged with emotion of some kind, full of purpose. That is why we have acquired it.” Here, Lanham suggests that charged information holds an attraction for a reader by virtue of its author position or bias, its attempt to persuade a reader, or its reach. Affect is an integral part of the reason why a reader may seek out information, and may be the reason that information grabs a reader's attention.

Mackey (2007) noted,

Attention is shaped by experience and fuelled by affect; it manifests itself in different parts of the body, in the limbic system of the brain, and in the conscious processes of thought. Attracting, sustaining and directing attention is a major thrust of any

text, whether designed for aesthetic, informational or commercial purposes, or any amalgam of the three.

Any presentation of information comes with a set of cues that suggest whether or not it can be trusted, according to the end reader / viewer. Sundar (2010) notes that these cues are also called heuristics, and can be defined as the signals that a user recognizes, which allow her to make a judgment without cognitively considering other characteristics of the information source. The motivation to pursue cognitive evaluation of an information source—referred to as “systemic processing” by Chaiken (1980)—is influenced by different factors. People have two different modes of processing: the heuristic and the systematic. The heuristic method of processing relies on cues for judgments that are stored in the memory of a viewer or user. It is informally known as the “top down” method of processing. The systematic method of processing relies upon cognitive judgments, and the active evaluation of the information or object at hand, in order to come to a judgment (Chaiken 1980). This is informally known as the “bottom up” method of processing. Clearly, an individual will build up a suite of heuristics over her or his lifetime, based upon other information objects she or he has encountered and judged. An individual will build stereotypes based upon her or his experiences. The more she or he has encountered particular stereotypes, the stronger the resulting heuristic cue for that person.

Reading research is relevant and important here, and serves as a reminder of the complexity involved in communication and learning. Reading theories contribute important concepts to my proposed research, particularly Rosenblatt's (1982) theories of reading stance: efferent reading and aesthetic reading. She suggested that one of these two stances predominate when a reader approaches a particular text at a particular moment in time. In the process of efferent reading, a reader “will narrow his attention to building up the meanings, the ideas, the directions to be retained; attention focuses on accumulating what is to be carried away at the end of the reading.” In contrast, aesthetic reading allows “a much broader range of elements will be allowed to rise into consciousness, not simply the abstract concepts that the words point to, but also what those objects or referents stir up of personal feelings, ideas, and attitudes.” It is extremely important to note that a single text may be read from either of these two stances; Rosenblatt (1991) firmly dismisses any suggestion that the text itself determines a reader's response: “We can read aesthetically something written mainly to inform or read efferently something written mainly to communicate experience. Our present purpose and past experiences, as well as the text, are factors in our choice of stance.”

Within each of these modes exists an opportunity for heuristic cues which either could signal the way in which the mode is meant to be interpreted (e.g., the use of the colour yellow to prompt joy or cheerfulness from a reader / viewer), or could signal that the mode is being employed (e.g., the blue text and underlining of a hyperlink, which suggests interactivity or hypertextuality). To this end, modal heuristics may

relate to a reader's / viewer's assigning of credibility to an information material.

However, as Sundar (2010) warned, “a chasm exists between our expectations about and the effects of digital media, and between our perceived needs and actual use of their offerings.” He used the example of digital media designed for young people, in which he has observed that much attention has been placed on the affordances meant to “dazzle” young users, but which do not result in long-term interest, learning, or use. This example suggests that it is important to avoid the mistakes of technological determinism when considering the design of media for young people (as well as for adults): the development of a particular affordance in the design of information material must work effectively, and on par with the development of the information material's contents. Simply addressing user attention is not going to guarantee interest or use. Heuristics do not necessarily adhere to a standard of credibility or design, and are not “proof” of the quality of the content to which they are attached.

It does seem that heuristics have notable and immediate impacts on media readers / viewers / users. Sundar (2010) quoted Metzger in stating that many people rely most heavily on the elements of design or presentation as heuristics for credibility assessment. And yet, it is extremely complex to understand how design works with readers and users. Lavie and Tractinsky (2004) assert, “The very broad scope of design possibilities, the creative nature of design work, and the almost unbounded relationships between design elements make it extremely difficult to isolate specific design aspects which may be considered aesthetic or which may influence aesthetic perceptions one way or another.” Adjacent to the complications of the interactions of design elements is the Persuasion Knowledge Model (), which outlines that much of the user experience literature presumes end users as not thoughtful readers of products: “they are seen to read the product, but not to recognize that the product has been written.”

RESEARCH METHODS

For the research, I am taking up to five information materials on the subject of the environment, aimed at young readers (between the ages of 11-17). The materials' approach to the subject varies, as some of my selections are scientific, and others focus on consumer or lifestyle choices that impact the environment. I am choosing specific materials for both their individual characteristics, and for the way in which they create a small “collection” of materials. When choosing an individual resource, I consider whether the material is print or digital, colour or black and white, large-format or small-format (for the print materials), and illustrated or primarily textual. I will also consider the interactive affordances each material offered to a reader / user (e.g., an online game as opposed to an online video). Collectively, I will review my collection of materials to determine the extent to which they contrast one

another. I want to ensure that each material sample is reasonably distinct from the others I have chosen. See attached JPEG files for examples of information materials.

Prior to our meeting, I will have asked each of the young people participating in my research to come to the pre-arranged session prepared to show myself and the other participant an "item" that they particularly like: a book, a game, a website, an app. I will ask each person to talk about the item that she or he has brought, to briefly discuss why this item appeals to her or him. I will ask each young person to respond to the others' selections. This action serves to shift the methods towards a research process that has some focus on the young people, as opposed to focusing strictly on the researcher's own questions. Barker and Weller (2003), in their work on "children centred research methods," note that there is benefit to engaging young people, through allowing them at least some space to talk about the things in which they are interested, not just those in which the researcher is interested.

I will then proceed to show the young people the information materials that I have gathered. I will ask the participants to follow a "Think Together" method while they look at the items in front of them. Branch (2006) defined "Think Togethers" as "small-group concurrent verbal reports." Branch noted, "Researchers can combine Think Alouds, Think Afters, and Think Togethers with additional data-collection methods such as observations, audiotape recordings, and/or video recordings to enhance the overall picture of adolescents' experiences during instructional activities."

I will sit with the designers in a ninety-minute session, and will ask them to review the information materials previously described in this proposal. I will ask them to look at the materials and talk about the heuristics they notice, and to discuss their interpretations of the design choices made with those materials. After the review, I will conduct semi-structured interviews to ask several questions about designers' decision-making processes when they design information materials for young people. I am not specifically seeking out designers of environmental materials for young people, nor am I seeking out the designers of the specific materials, which I am showing to the young people. This is because the materials I am showing to the young people, while chosen with specific criteria in mind, are not singularly important as aesthetic artifacts. However, I may prompt designers for any examples of projects, which may illustrate their narratives about how they consider and realize the design of materials for young people.

I believe that my research will help me investigate how aesthetics connect to particular factors of looking at, seeing, and reading information materials; for example, how they attract and hold some people's attention, or prompt particular kinds of affective and/or behavioural responses (such as suggesting readability). Through my reading interpretations of sessions with young people and interviews with designers, I look to understand the convergent and divergent understandings of elements found in specific examples of graphic design between these perspectives.

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FLUI

PERCEIVING TIME AND SPACE THROUGH EMOTION

Rafaela Beraldi Zeidler, Janaína Mendes Bueno de Godoy, Ken Flávio Ono Fonseca
 UFPR - Federal University of Paraná, Brazil
 ✉ rafaela.zeidler@gmail.com, janambg@gmail.com, ken.fonseca@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Rui Barbosa square, located in the center of Curitiba, Paraná, Brazil, was defined as the focus of our project since it is mainly used as a passage area. Since it is a vast space with substantial crowd circulation and in need of revitalization, we saw the opportunity to design an object that awakes curiosity and self-consciousness among people that pass through this square. Flui is a modular installation that focuses on the interaction between the users and the surroundings in an ephemeral way, providing a brief moment of relaxation and the sense of belonging to the city. The result is a dynamic product that stimulates the connection of people with their surroundings. Furthermore, it aesthetically contributes to the square presentation, attracting the attention of those who do not value the fusion between the urban space and its citizens.

KEYWORDS: *product design, emotional design, installation*

OBJECTIVES

Urban installations have been progressively more exploited worldwide. Studies concerning aridity and tension of modern cities and their influence on human quality of life have increased. In this scenario, the Flui project concept was developed. Due to a tight routine, people travel in a hurry through the city, without contemplating their surroundings, without realizing their actions, establishing sameness and stress in their day-to-day lives. According to Giroto, “The human being has the right and the need to leisure and to a daily relief” (Giroto, 2009, p.15). This quotation expresses the essence of the project: to cause a transient smile during the use of the installation, an action with an ephemeral effect, that functions as a punctual improvement in the user’s stressful routine, breaking it and allowing the user to modify and interact with the public space.

Jaime Lerner, an important Brazilian architect and urbanist, coined the term “urban acupuncture” to define simple and punctual actions that result in improvements to the city and its citizens (Urban Acupuncture, 2003). In this project, we intend to do a brief “acupuncture”, making the passersby’s day more interesting and contributing to the public space. We

also intend to awake a provocation in the bystanders, to allow them to enjoy a moment of real consciousness, depicted in the exact instant they stamp their footprints and realize how their actions can impact the physical space and the society.

The perception is provided by a brief interaction between the user and the product, an installation placed on the floor, without the need to increase the permanence period in the square since the interaction occurs along the route.

Figure 1. Project concept (source: the authors)

PROJECT LOCATION

Once again, Giroto (2009) incites a relevant issue for the project - the rescue of the original function of squares. It is believed that inserting a new element in space can arouse the curiosity in the passerby, which can contribute to rescue the squares' purpose "The squares, being places that receive many bystanders daily, and are available for the enjoyment of all, should be more valued and have their original purposes rescued, becoming a mean of physical and psychological relief for the city and its people" (Giroto, 2009, p.7).

Thus, as a case study, a large downtown square in Curitiba, Brazil, was selected - Rui Barbosa Square. It once hosted major events and circuses, but today it is perceived as a bus terminal in the open. This square holds ideal characteristics for a case study: it houses 44 bus lines, resulting in a large flow of people walking in a short period of time, a factor that demands quick interactions and increases the visibility of the project.

Due to the large amount of people circulating, especially at peak times, it was necessary to perform a flow analysis to understand the dynamics of the square and establish a strategic location for the project application.

The mapping was done by an observational method: on different days and hours we visited the square and observed, annotated and photographed the crowd, identified its habits and sketched its flows. We also observed the square from the top, on the terrace of a nearby building. This procedure allowed us to obtain information required to understand the flow paths and densities and how flows were distributed (red lines

Figure 2. Rui Barbosa Square (source: internet)

in figure 3). This corresponds to peak periods in the square: the lunch hour (12:00 to 14:00) and late afternoon (17:00 to 19:00). After the flow analyses, it became evident that the area in front of the largest bus stop has the largest circulation of people and is, therefore, the ideal area for implementation.

Since the project is located in a public space, it is not restricted to a target group, but can be seen by anyone who passes by.

FLUI

Flui project consists of a modular hydrochromic floor installation. The modules are placed on the ground, over the walking area of the bystanders. Each module is covered with a hydro-sensitive ink layer, and has low relief line drawings. Together, they create a colorful pattern.

The modules are classified in three categories: the ones that release water, the ones that carry water, and the ones that disperse water. The water runs through the indents until it reaches the disperse modules, which is where the interaction happens. All modules are sensitive to water and the users can interact with the entire installation.

The Modules

Each module measures 70,0 x 70,0 x 3,0 cm. The low reliefs are 1,5 cm deep and act as communicating vessels, allowing the water to flow through the installation.

Figure 3. Flow analyses (source: the authors)

Figure 4. Modules specifications (source: the authors)

Figure 5. Releasing module and dispersing module (source: the authors)

Figure 6. Flui's colors (source: the authors)

The releasing water module has a different height – 8 cm instead of 3 cm – and a curved profile (figure 5). This configuration allows water to run more easily.

The disperse water module has an irregular relief to spread the water over the surface (figure 5). The amount of water is enough to moisten the shoe soles of passersby without causing discomfort.

Patterns and Colors

The product was developed in modules in order to solve production issues, such as maintenance and installation.

The different drawings in each module, enable various compositions so that different patterns can be created.

The colors selected and the organic drawings aim to transmit the sensation of calmness and render the surroundings less chaotic.

MATERIALS AND PROCESSES

PVC and Injection

The most appropriate material for the production of the modules is PVC (Polyvinyl Chloride).

According to the PVC Institute (2013), this polymer is resistant to fungi, bacteria, insects, rodents and most chemicals. It is also weatherproof (sun, rain, wind) and durable, making it ideal for outdoors environments.

The process selected was injection molding and five molds were used, one for each module. Since it is possible to add pigments to the resin during the process, each piece can have a specific color.

Hydrochromic Pigment

Hydrochromic ink changes color when it gets in touch with water.

The design consists of two layers of ink on top of each other. When water is applied, the top layer clears, revealing the color underneath. Few drops of water are enough to initiate the reaction. When the water dries (approximately 5 minutes), the original color of the ink is restored.

The hydrochromic pigment is a material that permits the color to appear when the surface is sensitized by water, and it must be applied superficially in all modules. This pigment is indispensable for the effective functioning of the project.

Tests were performed on a functional model to prove the efficiency of the pigment, and the results were positive. After several attempts, the ink layer remained identical to the initial piece.

How Does Flui Interact with the Bystanders?

The default modules are black (not sensitized), meaning no water is in contact with them. Water that is released through the releasing modules each five minutes runs through the indents, filling the installation and sensitizing the hydrochromic surfaces. As the black ink fades away, the underneath color is revealed. When the water reaches the disperse modules, it spreads through the installation. Whenever bystanders walk over the water, colorful footprints are left behind. Gradually, as the water dries, the black ink reappears and the footprints fade away.

The purpose of the project is leaving traces, which is a playful way to provoke people to realize the beauty of each moment and that public spaces can and should be places of interaction and expression.

Figure 7. Hydrochromic pigment on functional model (source: the authors)

Figure 8. Product operation (source: the authors)

Figure 9. Simulations use - users interacting with Flui modules (source: the authors)

Flui's purpose is to interact briefly with the bystanders of Rui Barbosa Square, without diverting them from their path or delaying their routines, but stepping in when they are mechanically walking from one point to another.

Daily concerns, duties, stress, are all factors which disconnect people from the surrounding environment and turn the urban context into a tense and arid place.

The idea of Flui is to provide a few seconds of joy for its users, by proposing a brief connection with the city; it is a little surprise that may be capable of awakening the perception of the need to pay attention and be part of the environment.

PROJECT INSIGHT

This project aims to subtly question our busy routine and its impact in our life. It seeks an objective way of contributing to revert this self-destructive process. Furthermore, it enriches the public space, contributing aesthetically to Rui Barbosa Square, and therefore rescuing one of its original purposes.

The project provokes emotions, stimulating people to discover themselves as citizen that interact with a public place, sharing their sensations and discoveries with strangers and becoming aware of how personal attitudes can affect each other. Thus, a mere place of circulation can acquire a new meaning, turning it into a space that leads users to reflect on questions otherwise not contemplated, such as how they can connect with the environment and the value of citizenship, demonstrating

how a simple use of emotion can generate a complex impact in society's actions.

The potential of this project lies in the fact that people will not have to deviate from their routines. Its functional dynamism, by the appearance and disappearance of footprints, makes Flui always a new experience, not being tiresome and repetitive.

CONCLUSION

The project consists of an idea, a proposal, that was tested in partial prototypes and validated through questionnaires and talks, but it has not been implemented in the square. Indoor tests were realized with mockups and functional models in order to prove the efficiency of the material and perceive people's reactions. The objective, that was to provoke a brief smile and connect people with the environment, was successful since surprise was usually the reaction observed.

As a point of improvement, it is possible to redesign the modules in order to explore different thicknesses in the reliefs, resulting in a better aesthetic appearance.

The main concept of the project is the simplicity of the emotions generated, applied in a fast interaction between the users and the product. The project developed a punctual contribution, which integrates the city and the citizen, valuing the urban space and raising awareness on the impact of the inhabitants on the city.

Although the study was conducted at Rui Barbosa Square, the concept can be adopted in similar places around the globe in order to revitalize the environment and people.

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FEMO: EMOTIONAL DESIGN FOR KIDULTS

Diana Catalina Garzón Rodríguez
Pontificia Universidad Javeriana
✉ diacatalinagarzon@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the problem of kidults immersed in the media. An emerging global market, their needs, their appearance in Colombia, and how through emotional design, the theory of emotions, and Kansei engineering, the result is the design of a product that embodies all emotions and seeks to keep them away from immersion in the media, and to set goals and projects through their hobbies.

KEYWORDS: *emotional design, kidults, Kansei, emotions, hobbies*

INTRODUCTION

Some people always miss the days when they were teenagers, when they did not have big concerns, and maintain the lifestyle of those days, no matter how much time has passed since then. Not only do they keep objects from those days, their attitudes are the same and so are the decisions they make.

These kidults, whose behavior is not in accord with their age, are a new worldwide growing target which experts believe is an opportunity. Their capacity to keep interested in a beautiful appearance and in the fun of every detail is what makes them such a striking target. It is a completely emotional target.

Life is full of emotional moments, which are very intense. In those moments, people are influenced by their feelings about an object. The recreational, the beautiful and the emotional aspects must be included in every person's daily life. All these aspects are inherent in the lives of kidults. These conditions give rise to this project, that proposes to create an emotional object which has an influence on kidults from the very beginning and helps them to enjoy life through new experiences and goals.

BACKGROUND AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The Kidults

They are both male and female, but mostly male, aged 25 to 39 approximately, who do not wish to leave the comfort of their parental home. They fear what they might face without that atmosphere. They are narcissistic and individualistic;

they do not want emotional commitments. They continue meeting their friends to play video games and keep mementos of classic characters, such as those of Star Wars. They are consumers of products for children and teenagers, such as Lego and Cartoon Network or Nickelodeon channels. They still use teenagers' vocabulary (Lancheros, 2011).

This recent global trend is called "adultescents" in Spanish-speaking countries, "nestlings" in Germany, "parasitic singles" in Taiwan, and "kidults" in the United States (kids + adults).

Moreover, Nielsen Company¹ discovered this group of people in a study of television audiences in 2003. The results showed that people between the ages of 18 and 39 watched Cartoon Network more than those who watched CNN.

Since 1970, the percentage of young people around the age of 26 who live with their parents has increased 11% to 20% in the United States. (Hume). "The longest occupied nests in the world are in Latin America, with an average household output of 28 to 30 years", says Maritza Sandoval². (Lancheros, 2011)

Studies have shown scientific reasons for these situation. The Institute of Cognitive Neuroscience at University College, London, found that the brain continues its maturation process for 30 or 40 years (Blakemore, 2011).

Socioeconomic circumstances also have an influence. In today's world, people need to be better prepared for a job, which means they have to invest more time in their studies

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- 1 Nielsen Company is a world leader in market research and information.
 - 2 Director of the Master's Program in Consumer Psychology at Fundación Konrad Lorenz, Bogota.

and therefore go on living at their parent's home. Some kidults who live with their parents work, but make no contribution at home. There are also some who already live apart, but still depend on their parents economically.

In Colombia and Latin America, kidults belong to the higher socioeconomic strata and live in the midst of comfort.

There are no exact figures on how many kidults are in Colombia, but there are projections: according to DANE, in 2005 there were 9'357.000 people aged 25 to 39 in Colombia, and by 2020 there will be 11'594.030.

According to a survey done for this project in Bogotá, kidults of strata 4 and 5 feel their job is monotonous and demanding and get bored at home, although they remain there; they spend much time in the media world, especially socializing in Internet, and their goals and objectives are displaced because of that. They have a saving capacity, like collectible objects and invest in products related with hobbies, image and technology. Their main hobbies are music, photography and audiovisual aids.

Given the above, this project considers as key words: Monotony, obligation, boredom, dependence on the media world.

Definition of Emotions

Figure 1. Theory of Emotions According to Plutchik. It shows the eight basic or primary emotions with their opposite emotion, intensities and the emotions that arise from mixing them.

According to Galimberti (2002), emotions are mood disturbances or intense and brief affective reactions, which are determined by an environmental stimulus and accompanied by somatic conditions.

To understand emotions, Plutchik (1983) raises the above theory (Figure 1). He talks about eight basic emotions: joy,

anticipation, anger, disgust, sadness, surprise, fear and trust. Each one with its opposite and at different intensities, for example, the opposite of surprise is anticipation, surprise with more intensity is amazement, and with less intensity is distraction. From mixing them, other emotions arise. He calls them dyads, which are two primary emotions and their resulting emotion, for example, joy + surprise = delight, and trust + surprise = curiosity.

With respect to the general behavior of emotions, Plutchik (1983) suggests a process, in which the emotion arises from a stimulus, undergoes a process of cognition, reaches the emotional state and generates a behavior and a desired effect.

Emotional Scheme

Emotional design stimulates emotions and seeks to reach people, what they are, what they feel, because objects not only have practical but also symbolic functions. They evoke memories and feelings, and people identify with them. Emotional design brings people closer to their objects. People obtain pleasure from their use maintain an emotional state of enjoyment during the day.

Emotional design helps users feel more imaginative. "Emotions change the way the human mind solves problems" (Norman, 2003). When people are happy and relaxed, they are more creative and imaginative, their cognitive processes are broader; they perceive the general and not just the details.

Three emotion levels are involved in the design of an object: visceral, behavioral and reflective (Norman, 2003). Visceral design is the initial impact of a product, its appearance, touch, and the feelings it produces. Behavioral level is the use, the experience (function, performance and usability) (Norman, 2003). The reflective level implies consciousness, interpretation, understanding and reasoning. "Reflexive design is about relations that can stand for a long period of time, about the sensations of satisfaction which are produced when we own a product and can show and use it, and at this level the interaction between the product and our identity is important." (Norman, 2003)

Product design of this project will give more strength to the visceral and reflective levels, bear on appearance, identity and display; it exhibits and reflects an image by holding the object, aspects of kidults personality.

Kansei Engineering

Kansei engineering was created by Mitsuo Nagamachi to capture the feelings and emotions of humans in the development and design of a product. "It's a technology that joins Kansei (feelings and emotions) with the discipline of engineering. It is a field in which the development of products that bring happiness and satisfaction to humans is technologically presented through the analysis of human emotions and their incorporation in the product design" (Nagamachi, Mohd, 2011).

With this engineering, users give descriptive tags that identify desired product attributes, which are associated with words, images, shapes, colors, etc. that will be part of a product.

Figure 2. Analysis of the issue

THE ISSUE

Through target research, it is concluded that excessive use of the media world is the cause of kidults' feelings of monotony, obligation and boredom. So according to Max Neef (1998) kidults miss amusement, fun, pleasure and freedom.

According to the Theory of emotions and Kansei engineering, this project pretends to stimulate the emotions of trust, joy and surprise, through a new product that keeps kidults away from the media world and allows them to live new experiences, through goal setting.

So this leads the project to two key points:

1. To potentiate needs of leisure, identity and freedom
2. To stimulate the emotions of trust, joy and surprise

To satisfy the need for leisure, the product is expected to encourage kidults to be curious and imaginative; to get involved with the game; to allow them to dream, to relax, to play and to have fun; to go to meeting places in their leisure time.

To satisfy the need for identity, the product is expected to encourage kidults to feel part of a group, to feel coherence, to have self-esteem, to be integrated, to be in spaces where they feel part of a group, and to feel that their symbols are reflected.

To satisfy the need for freedom, the product is expected to encourage kidults to be independent, passionate, rebellious and tolerant and to risk.

With respect to the above-mentioned emotions, the product will stimulate trust in the kidults, making the product a reliable

means to guide them to achieve goals through their own hobbies. The product will stimulate joy and surprise from unexpected experiences in order for kidults to experience pleasure.

This project aims to provide kidults with a new opportunity for fun and amusement, proposing a more human and real contact with others through hobbies and interests other than the media world. It aims to make kidults happier and more creative, because "when people are having fun, they concentrate on the general and not on the details, so they find solutions more easily" (Norman, 2005).

General Objectives

To generate a new option for fun and entertainment for kidults, encouraging them to spend more time doing activities outside the media world and helping them to accomplish goals related to their hobbies.

Specific Objectives

- To stimulate the emotions of trust, joy and surprise in kidults
- To identify form aspects, which stimulate emotions of trust, joy and surprise in this group
- To determine the aesthetic and symbolic look of the product for this type of target market
- To suggest activities that are not dependent on the media world
- To offer dynamic and changing activities
- To encourage kidults to accomplish their goals through their hobbies

THE SOLUTION

Femo complies with the relevant aspects: funny, feasible to produce, dynamic, emotional (dependable, joyful, surprising), transformable, socializing and self-centered.

Femo is a game that guides the user to live experiences by accomplishing goals through his three favorite hobbies such as audiovisual, photo and music activities.

This proposal consists of three collections, each one with a theme of three hobbies. Each collection consists of three Femos. Each Femo has ten figure-shaped holes in his head, one of situations, one of objects and one of amounts. The holes are projected as shadows through internal illumination on a vertical flat surface chosen by the user. Each Femo has a game card explaining the meaning of each figure-shaped hole. Each player turns the heads of the three Femos and each Femo randomly projects a figure. This means three different figures (situation, object and amount) are projected,

Figure 3. Femo three collections.

which set one of the 1000 different experiences that a kidult can live, while accomplishing his goals. The kidult, then, takes the respective game card (see figure 4) and reads what he should do.

When each goal is completed, the user progresses through the game board and the winner is the one that accomplishes the goals set by the game.

There are two options for buying the Femo. The first one: the kidult can buy a Femo, which comes with a card and a game board. This way he will have to share with two other kidults who also have a Femo in order to complete the collection of three and be able to play (see figure 5). The second option: the kidult can buy the complete collection of a theme and invite others to play (see figure 6).

The product is made of plastic (matt PVC) for two reasons: one is emotional --plastic is the material classified as fun (Bramstom, 2010), it provides a soft and warm texture that the user likes, and it stimulates the expected emotions (trust, pleasure or delight)-- and the other technical.

TESTING

It consisted of a questionnaire answered by ten kidults, while they were touching different possible materials for Femo and watching a digital product model. It was carried out to determine whether the perceptual attributes of the product and its function stimulate the emotions of trust and pleasure or delight (joy + surprise).

Conclusions:

- The color of the whole collection generates trust and kidults like it.
- With respect to the texture of the material, the shiny vinyl generates more trust and the matte vinyl, more pleasure.
- With respect to the weight of the material, the matte vinyl generates more trust and pleasure.

Figure 4. Situation game cards.

Figure 5. 1 Femo + 1 game card + 1 game board.

Figure 6. Femo complete music collection (three Femos, three game cards, one game board)

- The size of the product generates identity and pleasure, although kidults consider it a bit big to carry.
- The shape of the product generates trust, joy and fun.
- The function of the product generates trust, joy, fun and surprise.
- Kidults like the variety of possible activities they can do; they generate surprise and expectation when turning the Femo.
- They sometimes prefer socializing through Femo than Internet.
- Although kidults like all the activities planned for the game, they prefer those performed indoors.
- The user is not always required to perform with others the activities proposed by the game.
- Although the project is directed to a growing target, it may be a reduced one.

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EVALUATION OF THE CONCEPT

Strengths

- It is based on a new emerging target, which is an advantage because there are fewer products directed to this target.
- The project encourages kidults to live new and different experiences related to their hobbies.
- It generates real human contact, making kidults more sociable and less introvert.
- It lets kidults socialize and belong to a social group through their own hobbies.
- It makes kidults more creative and active and capable of resolving challenges through the game.

Weaknesses

- Because of time limits, the testing was only done with material samples and digital images of the product, therefore, the operating mechanism of the product was untested.

GIANT, A SOCIAL DESIGN PROJECT: ENHANCING THE BUYING EXPERIENCE IN HIGH FREQUENCY STORES (HFS) IN BOGOTÁ.

Jackeline Arango Zapata, Marcela Velásquez Montoya
Design Engineering Research Group (GRID)
Product Design Engineering Department
Universidad EAFIT, Medellín, Colombia

ABSTRACT

The Product Design Engineering Department (PDED) at Universidad EAFIT in Medellín Colombia, has been working around the concept of The Bottom of the Pyramid (BoP) in the region not only for communities with low income, but also for communities with problematical social situations. In order to use design as a discipline to solve social situations, the PDED has been developing different projects with the purpose of working with students and academics from different universities around the world, having as its main objective social innovation practices. These projects are structured to contribute to the “revolution in design” teaching as proposed by Polak (2008, p74) and transform the way design is taught with the aim of educating socially conscious students. This year (2014), twenty-five participants consisting of students and academics from Universidad EAFIT and Universidad de Los Andes (Colombia), TUDelft and The University of Amsterdam (The Netherlands), and professionals from the company Solutions Group S.A (Colombia), participated in the workshop GiANT 2014. The main goal of the project was “to enhance the buying experience in high frequency stores (HFS) in Bogotá – Colombia between the owner, the buyer, the distributor and brands, aiming for a sustainability boost of the HFS sector”. This paper outlines the project methodology and the results obtained in the two-week workshop.

KEYWORDS: *Social Innovation, Product Design Engineering (PDE), Bottom Of the Pyramid (BoP), Social Design.*

INTRODUCTION

The bottom of the pyramid (BoP) is a demographic segment composed of more than 4 billion million people around the world with annual incomes of \$2 daily (Prahalad, 2009, p.28). That is, two-thirds of humanity who remain excluded from the economic system. In addition to a low income, poverty is also manifested by a restriction of freedoms derived from belonging to a particular caste, ethnicity, gender, religion or social condition that limits opportunities for personal growth Prahalad (2011) identifies the BoP markets as a new source of radical innovation, not just in products but also in the whole business system. In Colombia, according to the latest census of The National Administrative Department of Statistics (DANE), population belonging to low-low and low income reaches 63.5% of total population (almost 50 million) in the country, and more than 80% of the total population lives on the minimum monthly salary (320 U.S Dollars).

The dynamics of today’s world impose big challenges to the people that live in it. Educational institutions – and more

specifically universities – represent the main players in society transformation, because they train the future workforce and the leaders of tomorrow. To contribute specifically to Colombian society, design projects with a social focus require activities that integrate different social, political, economic, environmental and cultural stakeholders. Acting consequently, since 2008, the Product Design Engineering Department (PDED), at Universidad EAFIT in Medellín Colombia, has been structuring projects around the concept of BoP.

In 2009 and 2010, the project “Help Manuel” took place in Medellín. Students and teaching staff from Universidad EAFIT and TUDelft worked together with small entrepreneurs from Medellín. Later in 2011, “Global Design for Kids” project was conducted with the contribution of international students from different product design engineering universities. With these past experiences, in 2012 a more mature model was created. It was called “GiANT” - Global Innovation Antioquia, an international collaboration project that aims to design, create and implement diverse services and products related to improve the quality of life of the community. During the past

six years, the developed projects congregated around 150 students, twelve academic staff, ten engineering and design professionals, seven educational institutions and ten supporting companies.

GiANT 2014 took place during two weeks and it gathered 25 participants made up of bachelor and master students; academics from different areas of the discipline of design and professionals of the industry. Different academic backgrounds and levels of participants created a diverse group: product design engineers, industrial designers, graphic designers, digital media and anthropologists. The project initiative was born with the involvement of “Solutions Group” a Colombian company with more than thirteen years of experience in Bogotá focus on the creation of Point of Purchase Advertising. Due to the company experience in the HFS (High Frequency Store) sector, Solutions Group and Universidad EAFIT proposed the 2014 project objective: “to enhance the buying experience in HFS in Bogotá between the owner, the buyer, the distributor and brands, aiming for a sustainability boost of the HFS sector”.

HFS or neighborhood stores are the top businesses in Bogotá among hair salons, restaurants, bakeries and others. The consumers prefer the assortment, variety and lend options that these stores offer compared to super and hypermarkets, according to daily buying habits. According to Fernando Gonzalez, the VP of Strategic Planning of Solutions Group, in HFS exists a high level of informality in business administration and personal relations. The stores are concentrated in a higher percentage on socio economic strata one, two and three (F. Gonzalez, personal communication, 21 of June 2014).

In order to fulfill the project objective, whilst taking into account the several actors, a number of research questions were proposed to participants as a guide for the develop-

ment of the project. These questions are shown in Figure 1.

Section 2 of this paper describes GiANT project’s methodology and shows how each stage contributes to design products and services that help to enhance the buying experience in high frequency stores (HFS) in Bogotá. Section 3, summarizes the results of each team according to the design tools and techniques used. Section 4 describes project conclusions and recommendations for future initiatives.

PROJECT METHODOLOGY

GiANT’s general process was defined by combining the best practices from past experiences with social design projects developed by PDED, and by recognizing the main stages of well-known methods and tools for designing and working with communities. Three specific existing methods were studied – HCD – IDEO Human Centered Design (IDEO, 2011), MCT – Market Creation Toolbox (DIBD, 2011), and CDC2 – Community Design Cooking (Arango, 2013). To accomplish the main goal and answer the research questions, the project was divided into seven stages, as shown in Figure 2: introduction, understanding, conceptualization, design, building, delivery and documentation. The project had a duration of two weeks, and during that time participants were expected to achieve the following objectives:

- Identify the needs and desires through the thoughts and feelings of the communities.
- Develop a set of project specifications for all the stakeholders: people, context and technologies.
- Explore and propose two and three dimensional solution ideas through creative questioning and experimentation,

Figure 1. Research Questions

Figure 2. GiANT process

within the guidelines of the GiANT project.

- Develop a detailed study of the ergonomics and anthropometric conditions for materials and processes that take into account concepts of sustainability and originality from a creative point of view.
- Propose a monitoring plan for the community, to involve responsible members so that the proposal is sustainable in time.

GiANT's academic staff, clustered together different tools and techniques in order to develop the process at each stage and make a selection into a "Useful toolkit" (See Figure 3) to facilitate the process according to:

- Context of immersion: two geographically defined sectors in Bogotá (Suba and Engativá)
- The HFS situation
- Lack of time (two weeks workshop)
- Different levels of academic backgrounds and knowledge of participants: bachelor students, master students and professionals.

Lectures and more detailed explanations given during the stages in order to guide the general design process. Figure 4 shows an example of detailed information of the technique

Figure 3. GiANT Useful Toolkit

the COCD Box (Byttebier & Ramon, 2009)

RESULTS

The group was divided into four teams named as follows: Group 1: Patacón Flow; Group 2: Salchichow; Group 3: Chicharrón Solvers; and Group 4: Empanadas. Figure 5 shows the main results of each group following Giant's general methodology. Focusing on enhancing the buying experience at HFS, students made presentations and physical models to share with the vendors and other important actors.

According to all project results, GiANT staff members decided to follow and continue with the implementation plan of Group 3: "The neighborhood recipe book", once the workshop was finished. For the evaluation of this proposal, a plan was made to perform a concept validation, and in this way, corroborate and document the experience generated with the proposal between the shopkeeper and customers and how it will enhance the buying experience at HFS.

The project validation consists in five stages that will be conducted according to the planned objectives and to fit the time schedule of five weeks: Week one: Discover; Week two: prototype implementation version one; Week 3: prototype revisited; Week 4: prototype implementation version two; and Week five: editing and communicating the results

Figure 4. Description of the COCD box technique (Byttebier & Ramon, 2009 p134)

Group 1: Patacón Flows

Design Statement

“Convey the perception of freshness and better quality in high frequency stores”.

Techniques used

Understand: Observing and Interviewing.(Personas, Day in Life and Supply Chain Flow)

Conceptualize: Metaphor, Mind maps, User Profile.

Design: Brainstorming, Brainwriting.

Build: Canvas Business Model, Prototype.

Product Concept

“De la finca a tu hogar” (*From the farm to your home*).

A platform that connects the farmers with the vendors which forms a new community (to connect the supply with the demand). This is recognizable for the buyers of the products, mainly by stickers and posters. Customers can see if a HFS is connected with the platform and will trust the freshness of the products.

Group 2: Salchichow

Design Statement

“Create visual identity to connect HFS and the community”.

Techniques used

Understand: Observing (passive and active), Interviewing (Manicure Method).

Conceptualize: Metaphor.

Design: Brainstorming, Brainwriting and Bodystorming.

Build: Implementation plan. (Searching urban artist, searching HFS in the same neighborhood, inspired artists, artists in action, “Let them see us”, “I Belong” .

Product Concept

“Tiendarte”: A network that connects all the HFS owners through a visual resemblance achieved by local artist. An artistic work will be done on each HFS, based on the stories of the neighborhood and it will be linked to a webpage that collects all the artworks and shows the talent of the artist.

Group 3: Chicharron Solvers

Design Statement

"Create a new experience to keep and attract new customers and let the HFS seller be -the best neighbor- in the neighborhood".

Techniques used

Understand: Day in Life, Persona, Interview,

Conceptualize: Mind maps.

Design: Brainstorming, Brainwriting.

Build: Prototypes.

Product Concept

"El recetario de barrio" (*The neighborhood recipe book*)

A product that includes a set of cards, that can be filled in by the customers of the HFS with a recipe. The idea is to create a social recipe huddle that allows a free exchange of recipes. The ingredients could be purchased at the HFS. It helps to have better relationships tender-customers and increase sales according to be a cheap and seasonable ingredients.

Group 4: Empanada

Design Statement

"Create a shop-layout in HFS that goes with the daily routine of the customer".

Techniques used

Understand: Observing and Interviewing.

Conceptualize: Mind maps, User profile.

Design: Brainstorming, Brainwriting and Bodystorming.

Build: Prototype, storyboards.

Product Concept

The concept consist of two aspects: (i) a tool to measure the sales and (ii) a unit to display the products:

1. An app for a tablet or smartphone that helps the tender to keep track of who buys what and in what moment.
2. The display is designed to display the products in a really easy way. All the products can be displayed in crates to enable to tender to move the products easily.

CONCLUSIONS

This article describes GiANT 2014 as a social design project centered on the experience gained on previous projects developed (Help Manuel, GDK and GiANT) by the PDED at Universidad EAFIT and the collaboration between a variety of academic staff members of different universities and Solutions Group S.A as an industry partner. Different academic backgrounds and levels of participants created a diverse group that allowed a rich experimentation with an exchange of design techniques and methods that challenge every participant to analyze and expand their own approach to social design projects. Although a selection of tools were given to participants, depending on the level of knowledge on this and the expertise on the HFS topic, each group decided to use the tools that worked for them, and which will guide them best through the design process.

As an international collaboration project, GiANT creates an opportunity to redefine professional careers with a more open-minded approach according to discoveries about the culture, social differences, language barriers, and design perspectives etc. The intense workshop was a great opportunity for participants to get a detailed overview of the cultural context of the two selected sectors in Bogotá (Suba and Engativá), and in this way, to gain inspiration and to experiment with different tools and techniques in order to design for a specific community. One of the key elements is that the immersion in context allows a better understanding of the authentic community needs and, as a consequence, a better design solution that will impact positively on the community involved.

Participants were invited to live, work and play together on an everyday basis in an unfamiliar environment. They learned how to deal with uncertainty in so far as not everything was written on the project guide or given to them in detail in order to succeed in the process. The learning experience expands beyond the lecture rooms into every aspect of their lives. The project offers new challenges for students, academic staff and the industry. Participants can live in other cultures and explore their design, industrial and commercial processes. Universities and Industry could collaborate

like this in other topics towards a common goal and, in this way, promote students and professionals in the industry with a more international education with a social responsibility vision. Some limitations of the realization of this project included: an heterogeneous group with different professional stages (undergraduate, master students, professionals, and academics) that demanded to have a clear common goal, had to deal with language as a barrier of communication within each team, as well as with the community involved.

Project validation is a required phase that, due to the lack of time during the project, should be developed after the workshop with a clear refinement of responsibilities from the authors and the involved actors.

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THE AURA OF THE DIGITALLY FABRICATED

Jussi Ängeslevä, Michael Burk

Universität der Künste Berlin

✉ jussi.angesleva@iki.fi, m.burk@udk-berlin.de

KEYWORDS: *digital fabrication, computational design, product-service-systems, experience design*

INTRODUCTION

This workshop explores the meaning embedded in our everyday products, and how the digital manufacturing with CNC machining and 3D printing are changing the possibilities in embedding personalized content in the artefacts. Combined with the traditional handicrafts, but augmented with the digitally controlled, the resulting products can reflect the meaning of all parties, the designer, the process of making, and the end-user.

VISION

The workshop deals with the question of how we assign meaning to the things we live with. Traditionally, the hand-made aura is a valuable meaning-making factor, just as the precision quality of the mass-manufactured object. With the possibility of having the precision of a machine-made product, and the uniqueness of an atelier service, digitally fabricated artefacts balance between the different aspects of the meaning, of the aura of the artefacts. This kind of meaning making needs new kinds of production networks; new product-service-systems, that leverage internet, machines and traditional crafts.

BACKGROUND:

Two case studies are used to inspire discussion and projection in the local cultural context, to find out in which kinds of products the promise of the digital fabrication can best be utilized.

1. Locatable

Locatable is a dining table which has a carved street network filled with resin on it. It is meant to be ordered online with a simple interface, where one only has to specify a single address. The address defines the cutout area from the OpenStreetMap database, which gets sent to a 3D milling studio. The tool bit has been previously defined for optimal aesthetic, and the vacuum table under the milling machine makes it extremely easy and fast to carve the street network on a wooden board. Once ready, the board is transported to another wood working studio close-by, where the grooves are filled with epoxy resin and subsequently sanded for the final aesthetic, before sent to the client. A map as a motif is both useful and aesthetically appealing, a location is often emotionally charged, and both present an optimal content for a personalized product.

2. Ciphering

<http://ciphering.me>

Ciphering is a piece of jewellery, whose form directly represents the message encoded in it. A simple web interface lets the client configure a date and two initials as well as the diameter of the ring. Based on these variables, software algorithm generates the 3D form. When the slits on its surface are aligned, it reveals the hidden digits that define its form, either casting a shadow, or seen as a silhouette on its surface.

The manufacturing process combines the old and the new: First, the forms are created with a lost-wax casting process using a high-resolution 3D wax printer. The 3D printed wax model is put in a container and liquid plaster is poured around it to

locatable.beta

Step 1:

Show Place

Step 2:

please enter your e-mail address and details so we can send you a price offer.

Send me a quote

Credits

Hybrid-Plattform.org UdK Berlin TU Berlin Betten Bartmann Masonyte Recoltoir

FALTAN CRÉDITOS
DE IMÁGENES

create a mold. After the plaster sets, the wax is melted out in a furnace, and molten silver or bronze is poured into the plaster mold. The plaster is then pulled away to reveal the noble metal, and the finished product is polished for a smooth surface.

The designer is responsible for the general form but the "meaning" is cast by the client.

EXPECTED AUDIENCE:

The workshop participants are expected to discuss the implications of digital manufacturing in the local context of handicrafts and design. After the introduction to the theme, small groups are assembled and ideas are sketched for potential explorations for product concepts, which resources they will employ, and how the information flow will be choreographed.

The results are assembled together to portray the range of possibilities to leverage digital manufacturing techniques to create a new kind of aura for customized products.

The workshop can host up to 14 participants. The relevant disciplines for the attendees range from product design, graphic design, and architecture to digital media, web development and design engineering.

SPACE NEEDED FOR THE WORKSHOP:

A room with a projector, or a big screen for the presentation. Tables to sketch out ideas on paper in small groups (a studio setup is preferred over a lecture-hall type spatial arrangement), and, if possible (but not mandatory), a short visit to a workshop with a milling machine or a 3D printer.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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SKINTIMACY

TOUCH AS DIGITAL INTERACTION AND THE EXPLORATION OF INTIMACY

Alexander Müller-Rakow, Juan Pablo García Sossa
 University of the Arts Berlin, Design Research Lab
 Einsteinufer 43 – 53, 10587 Berlin, Germany
 ✉ alexander.mueller@udk-berlin.de, elmaildecorreos@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Skintimacy is an interface that allows for the collaborative manipulation of electronic-based processes through touch. Depending on skin contact, movement and duration of touch, digital and electronic setups can be influenced and controlled. In order to provide diverse opportunities for a playful control of audio, video, motors and other forms of output, a microcontroller is being employed to transfer data to software platforms. This sensor, acting as both a research tool and DIY kit (www.skintimacy.org, 2013), is intended to facilitate the symbolic relationship between physical computing and the sense of touch. The straightforward design of the device allows for experimentation in many different contexts. Taking into account the dynamic nature of skin conductivity, which varies individually, one has the possibility to create highly responsive installations.

In the first part of the workshop we will introduce the participants to haptic and touch-based interfaces, describe our intentions, the qualities and technical characteristics of the Skintimacy kit. In the second part, we will practically conceptualize and design interactive scenarios with the skin-based sensor in order to experience interpersonal touch as digital interaction and its influence on intimacy and personal boundaries. A common discussion on the potentials and limitations of skin-based and "techno-organical" interfaces will close the session.

KEYWORDS: *Interaction Design, Skin-based Interfaces, Experimental Interfaces, Touch, Intimacy*

BACKGROUND

After HCI research advanced the relevance of embodied interfaces (Dourish, 2001) and technological developments are providing electronic devices that are worn continuously closer to the person, traditional physical borders between the human body, and technical devices are about to disappear (Spren, 2010). This transformative process of shifting borders, induce amongst other social and psychological phenomena, a new spectrum of 'in betweenness'. Novel interaction scenarios will not only emerge between instruments and humans, but also between humans among themselves. To raise awareness, attach value, and add importance to these alternative interfaces, the artistic and scientific activities and works contribute to a constructive debate. For example, the oeuvre of performance artist Stelarc radically emphasizes his claim for a revised understanding of the role of the human body within a digitalized

world (Hauser, 2008). Referring to the skin as a central computer input, research projects like Skinput (Harrison et al., 2010) and Sixth Sense (Mistry et al., 2009) adduced technological evidence of its practicability.

APPROACH

Introduction (Phases 1 and 2)

The workshop serves as an overview of current research and developments of gestural and touch-based interfaces as well as referring discussions about experiential aspects, field of applications and limitations. By introducing the Skintimacy sensor that is being used in the workshop, we present the phenomenon of skin conductivity, its technical setup, and its potential to be applied in conjunction with the Wiring or Arduino

platform. Furthermore, in order to investigate the social relations in everyday life, the utilization of research tools within a frame of open source and DIY approaches (in contrast to studies in a laboratory) will be highlighted.

Making (Phases 3 and 4)

Designing scenarios has become an effective method to project, discuss and picture future use situations of technology (Iacucci et al., 2000). In the making phase the participants will first design use scenarios: short narratives within a specific context in which a gestural or touch-based interaction takes place. Each scenario will be analyzed identifying the actors involved, their relationship between each other, and the relevance of skin and touch in the experience. New possible scenarios will be proposed and will be briefly documented in phone videos or storyboards. At this point, the most important inputs and outputs will be identified, and the prototyping phase will begin, starting with quick lo-fi prototypes and 'hands-on' tinkering with the Skintimacy kit (Figure 1).

To enable all participants, each with different capabilities in the field of soldering and programming, to build working prototypes, we will prepare different hardware setups and provide a set of project samples and tutorials. Thus, each participant will be able to explore the skin-based interface, depending on his/her interests and individual skills.

Figure 1. Skintimacy kit

Figure 2. Testing with prototype

Reflection (Phase 5)

Finally, all participants will present the concepts and prototypes that have been made during the workshop in brief. In this phase, there will be a reflection and discussion about described ideas, individual experiences, and problems that shall raise the participants awareness of possible future scenarios and ethical issues of bodily-close, human-machine interfaces.

EXPECTED OUTCOMES

One learning objective is to present an approach for using physical computing as a method to experience and explore social interaction rituals with a focus on interpersonal boundaries and intimacy. We expect participants to get to know this 'designerly' mindset and discover new possibilities for skin-based interfaces, thus creating a shift in perspective on interface design and the potentials of embodied interaction.

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- 1 With this term we refer to Nigel Cross' "designerly ways of knowing" by which he means a design knowledge gained through creating, using and reflecting upon the use of artefacts. And especially "knowledge that is inherent in the processes of manufacturing.s"

CITY SOUND & EMOTION

THE CITY UNDERSTOOD AS AN EMOTIONAL SCENARIO FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF SOUND

Ivan Chaparro, Ricardo Dueñas

✉ ivanf.chaparron@utadeo.edu.co, info@resoundcity.com

ABSTRACT

This workshop is the result of a practice-based research, which explored several interrelated elements: first the theory of Psychogeography, applied to the creative representation of urban environments from a multilayered approach and from an emotional and psychological perspective; second, the exploration of sound and acoustic theory, as research tools and artistic possibilities, directed towards the analysis of public space, its documentation and understanding in relation to processes of identity, intangible patrimony and storytelling. And finally, an experimentation and technical research related to audio postproduction, real-time data processing and interactivity. This exploration lead altogether to the design of a persuasive experience that sought to communicate the research outcomes to a broader audience by means of an experimental performance and sound installation presented initially in several cities in the north of Europe.

BACKGROUND

This workshop is the result of a practice-based research which explored several interrelated elements: first the theory of Psychogeography, applied to the creative representation of urban environments from a multilayered approach and from an emotional and psychological perspective; second, the exploration of sound and acoustic theory, as research tools and artistic possibilities, directed towards the analysis of public space, its documentation and understanding in relation to processes of identity, intangible patrimony, and storytelling. And finally, an experimentation and technical research related to audio postproduction, real-time data processing and interactivity. This exploration lead altogether to the design of a persuasive experience that sought to communicate the research outcomes to a broader audience by means of an experimental performance and sound installation presented initially in several cities in the north of Europe.

Please take a few minutes to watch a trailer of one the previous performances carried out in Stockholm for an international art fair related to urban studies:

<http://www.resoundcity.com/human-mind-as-a-city/>

AIM

The main aim of the workshop is to illustrate the way in which the city, understood as a multifaceted system, can be abstracted and represented in relation to human emotions and therefore as a psychological-auditory scenario.

Different ways of walking through the city mean different narratives and perspectives and consequently different ways of thinking urban spaces.

APPROACH

The Workshop is divided in 5 stages as follows:

1. Introduction to the concept of Fragmentality (1 hour): namely, a form of urban exploration and documentation that involves walking by foot the streets of a given city collecting fragments in order to generate a posterior dialectical image through several methods of analysis. This initial stage is highly influenced by the practice of *flânerie* from the poet Charles Baudelaire, the work of the philosopher Walter Benjamin, the theory of Psychogeography,

the Situationist techniques and recent inter and trans-disciplinary practices carried out mainly in the north of Europe. All of them are taken as conceptual basis that outline the acts of walking and collecting as social and aesthetic disciplines.

2. The Derive (2.5 hours): Based on the conceptual basis outlined in the 1st stage, in the second step, the workshop participants have to stroll the streets in groups, following a simple set of rules while documenting their impressions with short text entries and sound clips. In order to capture the latter it is required of the participants that they have smartphones with GPS-logging and audio-recording features.
 - a. Sound collection: right after the workshop participants get back from their 'Derive', the organizers will collect and organize the audio files they collected in a collective archive; this will be the raw material for the final interactive experience.
3. Analysis and Storytelling (1 hour): the Derive carried out in the previous step is followed by a group discussion in which the impressions are shared and contrasted. Through several ideation techniques the goal is to generate a few collective narratives out of the short fragments of text collected during the walks.
4. Socialization and narrative crowd-ideation (1 hour): at this stage the different groups share the result of their impressions in the form of narratives, graphics, images, videos and so forth. Thereafter, the idea is to create a single narrative out of the stories presented by the different groups.
5. Interactive sound-experience (30 minutes): following the overall concept, the final stage is an experimental performance in which the audio-clips provided by the participants become the fragments in a collective and interactive composition, where the resulting soundscape responds to the brain activity of one of the participants, while connected to a neural actuator, therefore controlled by his or her emotions. The participant would be reading aloud the co-created narrative while the sound outcome would be matching his mental wandering through the text.

By using a Brain Interface, the concept of the final experience illustrates metaphorically the core of Psychogeographical theory, that is, a 'topographical model' that compares the human psyche with an imagined space, in order to make its complexity understandable. We intend to do the opposite, to create a sound-imagined space out of urban fragments, out of the brain activity of a person while performing a series of activities. It will be like thinking of a map from a given territory, which helps us to understand its geography, which, both like a mind or a city, has conscious, subconscious and unconscious areas.

The resulting performance would be a metaphorical Derive through a collection of urban sounds gathered collectively, by means of a brain scan device that measures specific brain waves while creating the sound composition.

NAMES, CONTACT AND AFFILIATIONS

Ivan Chaparro (primary contact)

Creative Director

Resoundcity Art Lab
www.resoundcity.com

Associate Professor

Jorge Tadeo Lozano University
Faculty of Arts and Design

Mobile: (+57) 319 2573243

emails: info@resoundcity.com

ivanf.chaparron@utadeo.edu.co

Ricardo Dueñas

Chief Technology Officer

Resoundcity Art Lab
www.resoundcity.com

Mobile: (+57) 317 8436111

email: info@resoundcity.com,

INTENDED NUMBER OF ATTENDEES (MAXIMUM AND MINIMUM)

Min 10, max 30

PLANNED DURATION OF THE WORKSHOP

full-day (6 hours)

PREFERRED CITIES

Medellín or Bogotá

SPACE/ROOM NEEDED TO CONDUCT THE WORKSHOP

1. A room for a screening, following debate and sound-performance:
2. Necessary equipment
 - a. Projector
 - b. Four studio sound-monitors (speakers) similar to these ones: <http://amzn.to/1fQJBb6>
 - c. Wires and connectors suitable to distribute them along the room, preferably in each corner (the idea would be to simulate the perception of spatial movement through a quadraphonic sound system)

MATERIALS AND SPECIAL REQUIREMENTS NEEDED FOR THE WORKSHOP

The assistants require the following equipment and tools:

1. A smartphone suitable for recording sound-clips in wav format
2. Headphones
3. Drawing materials: color-pencils, color-pens, markers

Ivan Chaparro

Designer and artist from Colombia, his artistic practice is located in the space between art, architecture, design and social research; considering technological media as wide, open-textured tools that help to reveal relations between material production and culture. Currently he is working as creative director of RESOUNDCITY and as associate professor at Jorge Tadeo Lozano University.

Ricardo Dueñas

Electronic Engineer from Bogotá, Colombia. Develops software and hardware for interactive installations and technology-driven art projects. Is co-founder of RESOUNDCITY, an urban research artistic laboratory. His recent works are related to e-textiles, sound art and dance.

JUST A MOMENT, PLEASE!

IMPROVING THE OVERALL USER EXPERIENCE, MOMENT BY MOMENT

Marco van Hout
SusaGroup, The Netherlands
✉ marco.vanhout@susagroup.com
Flin Nortier
Soda Studio, The Netherlands
✉ flin@sodastudio.nl

ABSTRACT

In this workshop a practical model (Moment-Message-Design) is presented to give designers who focus on the interactions with products the opportunity to explore the impact of the message on the 'conversation' (interaction) with the user. A focus on the combination of specific single moments, conversations and the (perceived) messages will enable designers to improve the overall user experience moment by moment.

KEYWORDS: *Conversational Design, Emotion, Interaction Design, Message, Moment*

INTRODUCTION

A couple of months ago, one of the authors went out to buy a gift for his wife. After browsing a couple of stores on the street, he ended up at a store where beauty and wellness products are sold. He found a nice set of perfumes and decided to purchase them. The lady behind the counter asked if it was a gift, and they had a short chat about the products and whom they were meant for, all while she was gift-wrapping them. After paying, she suddenly surprised him by getting from behind the counter, stepping up in front of him and presenting the gift in a nice looking bag in the way you would only present and hand-over something very valuable to someone. While doing so, she told him to enjoy giving this nice gift to his wife and looked him in the eye. These actions, combined with this personalized message, completely changed the overall purchase experience, from a cold transaction to a personal and even meaningful short interaction.

In this example, a real life interaction between customer and service provider was used to illustrate the power of a) a moment (paying), b) a conversation (about the payment, the gift and the purpose/meaning), and c) a personalized message

(attention to the client and understanding of the underlying goals) to achieve a specific emotional impact.

Even though the abovementioned example was about human-to-human interaction, similarities can be found in human-product interactions. For example, a focus on single moments in relation to product-use, referred to as 'micro-interactions' (Saffer, 2013). Examples of micro-interactions are: switching a product on or off, connecting one device to another, or changing a setting. In the abovementioned example, micro-interactions could be the act of paying, handing over the gift or the question of who the gift is for. Additionally, the concept of conversation is not new in the discipline of Interaction Design (e.g. Nickerson, 1976). Conversational design, as it has been referred to (Leong, 2004), is focused on designing human-product interactions that proceed as smoothly and efficiently as real-life conversations between people. Conversational design assumes that both the user and the product are *cooperating* in the conversation, also known as the cooperative principle of conversations. This assumption implies that both 'parties' can expect certain behavior from one another. For example, the product (and thus the designer) can expect the prospect user to have a certain level of knowledge before using it and engaging in the 'conversation'. A simple example is that a car

designer can assume the prospect driver has passed his or her driver's exam and therefore expect specific skills and behavior. Although both a focus on the specific actions in a single moment of product use (micro-interactions) and a conversational approach can be of great help in designing successful interactive products or services, they give little attention to the resulting emotional impact of the interaction and thus to that (important) part of the overall user experience. In this paper, it is argued that the intended message and especially the perceived message are key influences on the emotional impact of moments in human-product interactions, and should therefore be considered and explored by designers.

A practical model is presented to give designers who focus on the interactions with products the opportunity to explore the impact of the message in the 'conversation' (interaction) with the user. A focus on the combination of specific moments, conversations and the (perceived) messages will enable designers to improve the overall user experience moment by moment.

MOMENT-MESSAGE-DESIGN

To achieve the goal of gaining insight into the intended message of the design and its impact, a model that prescribes a specific design method has been developed: the Moment-Message-Design model. The model consists of three steps: 1) describing the *moment*, 2) conceiving a *message* and 3) creating *design solutions*.

The model intends to break conventional ways of following a (interaction) design process and create an opportunity to introduce new considerations, such as 'what's the message I want to communicate with my design?'. So, instead of regular product design thinking, "what more features can we add?", the question becomes "how can we tell our story better?". The model can help designers answering this question.

Figure 1: The Moment-Message-Design-model.

Step 1: The moment

In this step the designer describes the moment he is designing for as accurately as possible. For example, a customer of a telecommunications operator expects to receive a certain

mobile phone and finds a different phone is delivered. Now, a designer wants to create a solution so that both parties have a desirable situation as quickly as possible. The designer is to describe in detail all the key players of this moment and what their role is. This gives an overview of opportunities to intervene with a design, and makes way for the next step: Conceive a message.

Step 2: The Message

This is the most important step in the model. First, the designer consults his or her own feelings and emotions to formulate an intended message (e.g., by roleplaying). This should be kept as abstract as possible, for example, think about how instrumental music can deliver a message without the lyrics, or like the non-communicated intentions you feel during a conversation. This step is more about the intentions and empathizing with the situation than about the techniques to deliver the message. These techniques are left open as much as possible and are created in the next step: Create design solutions.

Step 3: Design Solutions

The message can be delivered in many different ways. This is the time where designers brainstorm about ways to translate it. For example, saying 'we're sorry we sent you the wrong product' can be written in an e-mail, told via a phone call or communicated in a humorous video about people making mistakes. But many more original and impactful ways are probably still undiscovered. By knowing your situation (moment) and the message you want to communicate, you get a large number of new opportunities for design solutions. As a brand or company, this could give you the advantage you need over competitors or, better still, show what's different and unique about you by more effectively communicating your vision.

WORKSHOP GOALS

This half-day workshop will provide (interaction) designers the opportunity to experiment with an approach that enables them to explore the impact of their design (message) in specific moments. The Moment-Message-Design model provides them with a practical framework to improve the user experience of their designs, but at the same time does not presume to have all the answers. The workshop is meant for designers of all disciplines; however, it is expected that the approach will mostly resonate with interaction designers, or designers with a specific focus on the interaction between product and user.

OUTLINE AND ACTIVITIES

1. Introduction to conversational approaches, challenges and opportunities.
2. The Moment-Message-Design model: Bit-sized theory and a description of the model. Short exercises to understand the model and experience the approach.

3. Case introduction: What's today's challenge? Groups of 3, exercise to apply the model.
4. Presentations: Show each other your results and what you've learned.
5. Closing statements.

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AFFECTIVE DECISIONS AND RECOMMENDER SYSTEMS

Juan José González, Mateo Ospina, Juan Salamanca, Héctor Mejía
Universidad Icesi

✉ jujogi413@gmail.com, mateo7845@gmail.com, jsalam@icesi.edu.co, hectorjaime.mejia@gmail.com

BACKGROUND

The rationale behind recommender systems is that people make rational decisions based on the available information they have in a particular context. However, substantial experimental data show that what people think, like, need or want is often influenced by the way their options are framed, deviating their 'rationality'. We aim to explore some principles of behavioral economics in the design of recommender systems through an empirical study based on a smart phone application purposely customized for the 9th Design and Emotion conference.

A rational decision is such that maximizes someone's current situation yet avoiding losses. Many situations of everyday life show that people often make "irrational" decisions because they make choices that procure greater benefits to others than to themselves. Such 'irrational' behavior might be defined in terms of cognitive biases and judgmental heuristics (Tversky & Kahneman, 1974).

From a comprehensive literature review of behavioral economics Pfarr and Gregory (Pfarr & Gregory, 2010) characterized seven relevant behavioral tendencies in decision-making. These behavioral tendencies are clusters of literature that have circulated significantly in behavioral economics discussions, and that they argue are relevant to design research. We find Context-Dependent Preferences and Affective-Cognitive Decision Making tendencies particularly relevant for the design of computational recommender systems. Context-Dependent

Preferences is the tendency in which people prefer intermediate options rather than those located at the extremes of a continuum (Simonson & Tversky, 1992). Context-Dependent Preferences are also related to the location of appealing or unappealing items in relation to each other. People perceive paired options with the same attractiveness as less appealing than the same options evaluated independently, but people perceive an attractive option as more appealing if it is paired with a non-attractive option (Hsee & LeClerc, 1998). Affective-Cognitive Decision Making is the tendency of people in situations of scarce information to follow their affective reactions rather than their cognitive reactions (Shiv & Fedorikhin, 1999).

The smart phone application to be ran in conference attendees' phones was developed in the Fall semester of 2013 using the database of presentations and the schedule of the 7th Design and Emotion Conference, held in Chicago in 2010. For the workshop we will use the schedule and database of presentations of the 9th Design and Emotion Conference. The application, named Day Book, allows users to program their conference schedule and share it with other registered attendees. The user has two ways of picking a presentation: by topic preference or by schedule availability. Moreover, the attendee can fine-tune the system's recommendation by checking the name of the speaker or the list of potential attendees to a given presentation. Such list of potential attendees is updated on the fly as people subscribe or unsubscribe to the presentation. The interface design takes into consideration the two behavioral tendencies mentioned above to present the recommended results.

Figure 1. Screenshots of the application displaying the list of presentations recommended by the system based on the attendee's preferred topics and availability. It presents some examples of the lowest decision making level of navigation. Source: the authors.

The general usability and task accomplishment of the application has been tested with seven users yielding very satisfactory results. However, the subjects in the user tests were not very familiar with the dynamics of parallel tracks conferences.

GOAL

We want to use D&E2014 as a living laboratory to explore three aspects of the application:

1. In what degree are academic attendees biased by popularity when choosing a presentation from an offered schedule?
2. In what degree are the choices of academic attendees influenced by the displayed schedule?
3. Is the user interface clear enough to help attendees to program their schedules?

The application will be a fully working prototype; therefore it would be a valuable tool for attendees to program their schedule and for organizers to make a post-mortem evaluation of the conference.

APPROACH

This workshop does not need a specific location; it is open to everyone who wants to install the application in his/her mobile phone, and could be held simultaneously in the three cities of the conference.

Potential attendees will be encouraged to download and install the app in their phones some days before or at their arrival to the conference. This could be a way to entice people to register specially if they are in Bogotá.

We would like to have a desk at the registration booth in Bogotá to inform people about the app and present some visualization of the conference's dynamics at the closing ceremony.

Users will be asked to accept the terms and conditions of installing the application. There will be a crystal-clear notification of the type and amount of data they will disclose to the workshop organizers and how we will guarantee the confidentiality of the data collected. We foresee that we are collecting only attendees names, conference ID, presentations marked as "I will attend", e-mail, website, affiliation.

The data collected will be used to study how some data structures such as lists and the organization of items in the list affect people's decisions. It will also be used to study the evolution of the presentation's popularity.

The app is not intended to advertise any organization.

NUMBER OF ATTENDEES

As many as registered attendees who download the app.

PLANNED LENGTH

The official days go from October 6-10, but since the app will be available one week before the conference begins, the total length would be ten days.

PREFERRED CITY

There is no need to be at a specific location. We would like to have a representative at the registration desk in Bogotá. We will also have a booth in Cali.

MATERIALS

Attendees smart phones, application, iOS, and Android compilers. Universidad Icesi will provide the server and other technological facilities.

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